

TILLARNI O'QITISH VA MADANIYATLARARO ALOQALARDA INNOVATSIYALARNI QO'LLASHNING AHAMIYATI

XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMAN

TOSHKENT, MAY 16, 2025

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
“INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL OF FINANCE AND TECHNOLOGY”
INSTITUTI**

**“TILLARNI O‘QITISH VA MADANIYATLARARO ALOQALARDA
INNOVATSIYALARNI QO‘LLASHNING AHAMIYATI”**
mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari

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**МИНИСТЕРСТВО ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, НАУКИ И
ИННОВАЦИЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН
ИНСТИТУТ “INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL OF FINANCE AND
TECHNOLOGY”**

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**«ВАЖНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИЙ В
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КОММУНИКАЦИИ»**

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Anjuman O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2022-yil 7-martdagi 101-f-sonli farmoyishi "O'zbekiston Respublikasida 2022-yilda xalqaro va respublika miqyosida o'tkaziladigan ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik anjumanlar rejasi" hamda "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi farmonlariga muvofiq tashkil etilmoqda.

Anjuman maqsadi: mamlakatimizda ta'lim va filologik sohalarda olib borilayotgan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarining samarasini ochib berish, professor o'qituvchilar, doktorant va mustaqil izlanuvchilar hamda talaba yoshlar orasida turizm sohasida tilning muhim jihatlarini targ'ib etish, til ta'limida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish, o'zbek va xorijiy tillarni qiyosiy o'rganish masalalarida ta'limning yetakchi mutaxassislar bilan tajriba almashish hamda ushbu sohadagi so'nggi tadqiqot usullarini ommalashtirishdan iborat.

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The conference is organized in accordance with Order No. 101-f of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2022 (“On the Plan of International and National Scientific and Scientific-Technical Conferences to be Held in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022”), as well as with the decree “On the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.”

The objectives of the conference include:

To highlight the outcomes of ongoing scientific research in the fields of education and philology in Uzbekistan

To promote the important aspects of language in the tourism sector among university professors, doctoral candidates, independent researchers, and students

To utilize modern pedagogical technologies in language education

To facilitate the exchange of experiences with leading specialists in the field of education concerning the comparative study of Uzbek and foreign languages

To popularize the latest research methods in this field

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Welcoming speech

Assalomu aleykum, participants and observers of our international scientific conference!

Dear esteemed guests,

On behalf of the International School of Finance, Technology, and Science, we are pleased to welcome you.

We warmly welcome you to the international scientific-practical conference titled "THE IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING INNOVATIONS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION" organized by the Department of Philology and teaching languages of our institute!

In today's rapidly growing era of globalization, efforts are being made to bring the teaching of foreign languages to a new level and organize systematic work to develop the field. This is all in order to educate the growing generation comprehensively, create favorable conditions for them, and implement large-scale work in the higher education system, just as in other fields. The closeness between countries and peoples, their mutual neighborly relations, and the results of strategic cooperation have created a foundation for citizens to travel the world and study new languages and cultures, which in turn has become the basis for the new humanitarian field of intercultural communication and tourism.

Furthermore, the introduction of effective teaching methods, programs, and textbooks that have yielded successful results worldwide into higher educational institutions is a clear example of this. The establishment of cooperation between our institute and foreign educational institutions is one of the vivid illustrations of this. This is because today's youth are expected to know not just one, but at least 2-3 foreign languages, as demanded by the times.

Our country, being one of the central points of the Great Silk Road, has a rich heritage, with our ancestors mastering languages such as Arabic, Persian, and Turkic. Moreover, today's process of globalization shows that language learning is not just a demand of the present day, but a necessity for us. We are descendants of writers and scholars who created in two, three, or even four languages. The blood of great scholars flows in our veins. While continuing their spiritual legacy, we must also focus on the growing importance of learning and teaching foreign languages.

It is also important to note that mastering any foreign language starts with a deep understanding of one's own native language. A nation that loses its native language loses its identity and national spirit. The President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has highly valued our native language, saying: "The Uzbek language is a symbol of our national identity and independent statehood, an invaluable spiritual treasure, and a great value."

On behalf of the ISFT team, we congratulate all the scholars and researchers gathered here today and once again welcome you to our institute.

I hereby declare the international scientific-practical conference on the topic "THE IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING INNOVATIONS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION" open.

Thank you for your attention
Rector of ISPT institute

**TILLARNI O‘QITISH VA MADANIYATLARARO
ALOQALARDA INNOVATSIYALARNI QO‘LLASHNING
AHAMIYATI**

**“BRIDGING CULTURES: INNOVATIONS IN LANGUAGE
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**«ВАЖНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИЙ В
ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ЯЗЫКОВ И МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ
КОММУНИКАЦИИ»**

**TILLARNI O‘QITISHDA INNOVATSION USULLAR VA
TEKNOLOGIYALAR**

**INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN
LANGUAGE TEACHING**

**ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В
ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ЯЗЫКОВ**

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON LANGUAGE AND IDENTITY

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Abstract: This article explores the profound effects of social media on language and identity in the digital age. Social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok, have significantly influenced how individuals communicate, leading to the evolution of language through new slang, abbreviations, and visual expressions like emojis. While these changes have simplified communication, they have also raised concerns about the decline of traditional language skills.

Additionally, social media provides individuals with the opportunity to craft and curate their identities, leading to both empowerment and challenges related to self-esteem and societal pressures.

Keywords: communication, digital culture, emojis, identity, language evolution, online personas, self-expression, slang, social media.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние социальных медиа на язык и идентичность в цифровую эпоху. Платформы социальных медиа, такие как Facebook, Instagram и TikTok, значительно изменили способы общения людей, приведя к эволюции языка через новые сленговые выражения, аббревиатуры и визуальные элементы, такие как эмодзи. Несмотря на то, что эти изменения упростили общение, также возникли опасения по поводу упадка традиционных языковых навыков. Кроме того, социальные медиа дают людям возможность создавать и курировать свои идентичности, что ведет как к усилению самовыражения, так и к проблемам, связанным с самооценкой и социальными давлениями.

Ключевые слова: общение, цифровая культура, эмодзи, идентичность, эволюция языка, онлайн-персоны, самовыражение, сленг, социальные медиа.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu magolada ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning til va shaxsiyatga ta'siri raqamli davrda o'rganiladi. Facebook, Instagram va TikTok kabi ijtimoiy tarmoq platformalari odamlar o'rtasidagi muloqotni sezilarli darajada o'zgartirib, yangi so'zlashuv uslublari, qisqartmalar va vizual ifodalarga, masalan, emojilarga olib keldi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar muloqotni soddalashtirgan bo'lsa-da, an'anaviy til ko'nikmalarining pasayishi haqida tashvishlar ham mavjud. Bundan tashqari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar odamlar uchun o'z shaxsiyatlarini yaratish va tasvirlash imkoniyatini taqdim etadi, bu esa o'zini ifoda etishda kuchayish va o'z-o'zini baholash va ijtimoiy bosimlar bilan bog'liq muammolarga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Aloqalar, raqamli madaniyat, emojilar, identifikatsiya, til evolyutsiyasi, onlayn-personalar, o'zini ifoda etish, sleng, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar.

Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok have dramatically transformed how individuals communicate and express themselves. These platforms not only provide new ways to interact but also have a profound impact on language usage and personal identity. As a result, digital communication has undergone significant shifts, influencing both how we speak and how we present ourselves in the online world. Social media has ushered in a new era of language, where

communication is often quick, casual, and abbreviated. For example, abbreviations like "lol" (laugh out loud) and "smh" (shaking my head) have become ubiquitous in daily conversations, showing how language has adapted to the need for speed and efficiency in the digital age. These shorthand expressions enable users to convey emotions and reactions quickly, reflecting the fast-paced nature of social media interactions. Emojis, which began as simple icons expressing emotions, have evolved into an integral part of online communication. These visual symbols allow users to convey complex feelings and reactions in a way that words often cannot. Emojis have become a universal language in digital communication, helping bridge cultural and linguistic divides and allowing people to express themselves beyond the confines of text. This form of visual communication plays a significant role in reducing language barriers, offering a shared understanding of emotions across different cultures (Danesi, 2016). While the rise of informal language and shorthand on social media has made communication more efficient, it has also raised concerns regarding the decline of formal language skills. Critics argue that the widespread use of abbreviations and informal language could lead to a reduction in proficiency in traditional writing and speaking (Baron, 2008). However, some linguists suggest that these changes reflect the evolving nature of language, which naturally adapts to new contexts and technologies. This argument posits that digital communication is simply a different, but equally valid, form of linguistic expression. In addition to its impact on language, social media also plays a pivotal role in shaping personal identity. Online platforms offer users the ability to curate their public personas, carefully selecting which aspects of their lives they wish to present. This ability to filter and edit images, posts, and videos allows individuals to create idealized versions of themselves that align with societal expectations or personal aspirations. However, this curated self-presentation can contribute to unrealistic portrayals of one's life, often leading to feelings of inadequacy and self-doubt among those who compare themselves to the "perfect" lives of others seen on platforms like Instagram (Fardouly et al., 2015). The pressure to conform to online ideals of beauty, success, and happiness can have a significant impact on self-esteem, particularly among younger users who are still developing their sense of identity. While social media allows for self-expression, it also fosters an environment where users are constantly evaluating themselves in relation to others, which can lead to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression. The concept of "personal branding" has also emerged on social media, particularly among influencers and content creators. Individuals now actively craft their public image to build a following and gain recognition, turning their online persona into a form of social currency. This phenomenon has created a new type of economy, where one's personal identity is commodified, and success is measured by the number of likes, followers, and engagements one receives (Khamis et al., 2017). While this offers opportunities for

personal empowerment, it also creates a pressure to constantly perform and meet the expectations of online audiences. Despite these challenges, social media has also empowered many individuals to express themselves more freely than ever before. It provides a platform for marginalized groups to share their experiences and connect with like-minded people. Through the use of hashtags and viral content, social media has become a tool for activism and social change, allowing users to raise awareness about important issues and create a sense of community around shared values. The influence of social media on language and identity is multifaceted, offering both opportunities and challenges. On one hand, social media has facilitated the creation of new linguistic forms and enabled users to express themselves in more creative and efficient ways. On the other hand, it has introduced concerns about the erosion of formal language skills and the impact of curated identities on self-esteem. As social media continues to evolve, so too will the ways in which language is used and identities are constructed. Future research will be essential in understanding the long-term effects of these digital transformations on communication and self-expression.

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USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES TO EFFECTIVELY TEACH ENGLISH

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Abstract: This academic paper explores the effective use of modern technology in English classes. With the rapid development of technology, teachers have the opportunity to combine innovative tools and methods to improve language learning and teaching. This article provides an overview of various modern technologies, including computer-aided language learning (CALL), mobile applications, online resources, and virtual reality (VR), discussing their possible advantages and challenges in teaching English. In addition, it offers practical strategies to integrate these technologies into the classroom, highlighting their impact on motivation, activism, language proficiency, and cultural competence. Through the use of these tools, teachers can create a dynamic

and interactive learning environment that helps them to master the language effectively.

Key words: opportunity, applications, feedback, language-related, improve, technology, interactive, multimedia materials.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola ingliz tili darslarida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishni o'rganadi. Texnologiyaning jadal rivojlanishi bilan o'qituvchilar til o'rganish va o'qitishni takomillashtirish uchun innovatsion vositalar va usullarni birlashtirish imkoniyatiga ega. Ushbu maqolada turli xil zamonaviy texnologiyalar, jumladan, kompyuter yordamida til o'rganish (CALL), mobil ilovalar, onlayn resurslar va virtual haqiqat (VR) haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan, ularning ingliz tilini o'rgatishdagi mumkin bo'lgan afzalliklari va muammolari muhokama qilingan. Bundan tashqari, u ushbu texnologiyalarni motivatsiya, faollik, tilni bilish va madaniy malakaga ta'sirini ta'kidlab, sinfga kiritish uchun amaliy strategiyalarni taklif etadi. Ushbu vositalardan foydalanish orqali o'qituvchilar tilni samarali o'zlashtirishga yordam beradigan dinamik va interaktiv o'quv muhitini yaratishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: imkoniyat, ilovalar, fikr-mulohaza, tilga oid, takomillashtirish, texnologiyalar, interaktiv, multimedia materiallari.

The integration of modern technology into education has revolutionized traditional teaching practice, including the field of teaching English. This article explores the possibilities of using modern technology to improve the results of learning English. It explores the benefits, challenges, and effective strategies of integrating these technologies into the classroom.

1. Computer-aided language learning (CALL)

CALL (Computer-Aided language learning) offers the benefits of using computer technology in language learning. These technologies include in-house online exercises, interactive multimedia materials, language learning programs, and virtual language labs. CALL offers several opportunities in language learning, such as individual reading, quick feedback, and the ability to practice language skills in a spontaneous and interactive way. CALL offers the opportunity to self-train the first preferred language skills in language learning. In traditionalism, teachers see difficulties in responding to several differential students at school. CALL, on the other hand, provides individual reading to meet students of different levels and provide them with customized reading instructions. This allows each student to master specific reading instructions and exercises, and also allows teachers to guide and present students. Secondly, CALL offers a quick feedback opportunity in language learning. In many cases, teachers can fix a problem with the timing and Article analysis to start the feedback process. CALL, on the other hand, increases the possibilities of feedback, as students do not perform various exercises to strengthen the rules of reasoning, spelling and grammar in time. This speed helps students develop language skills. Third, CALL provides interactive exercises in language learning. Interactivity is a factor that has importance for liking and motivating students in the learning process. Interactive exercises allow students to strengthen their practical language and master their work.

2. Mobile applications: Mobile applications have gained significant popularity

in recent years and offer many opportunities for language learning. The article explores the benefits of using mobile apps in English lessons, including their accessibility, flexibility, and gamified functions. It provides examples of language learning programs aimed at mastering vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, and reading comprehension. Mobile applications have become more popular for providing many opportunities in language learning, and the benefits of using them in English lessons are outlined in the article. Thanks to the convenience, flexibility and gamified functions of these mobile applications, students can achieve good results in the language learning process. Mobile applications play an important role in providing language learning accessibility. These applications are consumed through mobile devices and therefore all in one place for students, the time and place they need to reach. These apps allow readers to allows you to perform language-related exercises at a talented time and in their chosen place. Mobile applications will be very useful in providing flexibility for students. These apps allow students to connect with different organizations in the learning process, such as places close to our father, friends, and family members. These apps also allow students to provide a personalized learning guide and a collection of learning materials, and they also allow them to build and master interactions with students. It is also very important that mobile applications have gamified functions in language learning. They are used in learning through games, competitions and organizations to interest and motivate students. For example, games for mastering vocabulary, interactive tasks for checking pronunciation, games aimed at understanding grammar and reading. Make it interesting and convenient for students to learn the necessary knowledge through games through these applications.

3. Online resources: Nevertheless, mobile applications are becoming more applicable in language learning and they help students to increase comfort and motivation in learning language-related exercises. These applications allow students to master, learn, and consolidate their knowledge of language. There is a choice of flexible mobile applications for language learning with tips and references. The Internet provides several online resources to help improve English language instruction. These resources allow learners to provide original language materials, interactive exercises, and virtual language communities. These resources discuss the integration of language lessons into planning and are bullied in recommendations for choosing reliable and suitable resources. The resources that provide the original language materials are good resources for studying the grammar, vocabulary and vocabulary of the English language. Notable publications such as Oxford University Press, Cambridge University Press, for example, provide several English textbooks, dictionaries, and readable materials for students. Using these resources will help students understand and learn the language. The resources that provide interactive exercises allow students to learn the language in a practical way. Such resources allow

students to master and perform practical exercises. Through these exercises, students will be able to use the language, translate it, pronounce it and strengthen the rules of grammar. Platforms like Quizlet, Duolingo, BBC Learning English are good resources for interactive language learning. Resources that provide Virtual language communities allow students to integrate into online learning processes. These resources allow students to engage with online classes, interpretive opportunities, feedback forums, and learners. For example, online platforms such as italki, Verbling, Preply provide access to tutors and teachers for language learning. The resources that provide integration into lesson planning help students learn English in a short time. These resources help students organize classes, exercises, tests, and assessments. Online learning platforms like Google Classroom, Edmodo, Schoology are good options for organizing classes and managing students. When choosing reliable and suitable resources, it is important for students to choose the resources that suit them. In this case, the level of resource development, its relationship with students, methods suitable for students and educational goals should be observed. It is recommended to pay attention to the choice of convenient, practical and motivating resources for students. Online resources offered via the Internet allow language learning to be more efficient and interesting. The use of these resources helps students to increase their mastery and learning.

In conclusion, it can be said that the effective use of modern technologies in English lessons provides excellent opportunities to increase the results of language learning. Teachers can use computer-aided language learning, mobile applications, online resources, and virtual reality to create a dynamic and interactive educational environment that encourages student activity, motivation, and language proficiency. However, in order to maximize the benefits of these technologies, it is necessary to carefully consider integration strategies, teacher training and pedagogical foundations. As technology continues to progress, in the 21st century, English was introduced to meet the changing needs of students further research and research of innovative approaches to technology integration is necessary in teaching.

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USING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH WITH INTERACTIVE WHITEBOARDS AND ONLINE RESOURCES

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Abstract: The study explores the integration of technology in English language teaching, focusing on the use of interactive whiteboards and online resources. Technology has revolutionized traditional teaching methods, offering educators innovative tools to enhance classroom instruction and foster student engagement. Interactive whiteboards enable dynamic, multimedia presentations, interactive lessons, and collaborative activities, catering to diverse learning styles. Additionally, online resources provide access to a vast array of educational content, including language learning platforms, digital exercises, and authentic materials. These resources support both in-class and independent learning, encouraging language practice beyond the classroom. While the effective use of technology can enhance language acquisition and learner motivation, challenges such as technical issues and the need for teacher training remain. This paper emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach, where technology complements traditional teaching strategies. By leveraging the benefits of interactive whiteboards and online resources, educators can create an enriched, inclusive, and effective English language learning environment.

Keywords: Interactive whiteboard, internet connectivity, learning styles, classroom, students, online resources, technology in education, digital learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili ta'limida texnologiyalarning, xususan, interaktiv doskalar va onlayn resurslarning qo'llanilishi tahlil etilgan. Texnologiya an'anaviy dars usullarini o'zgartirib, o'qituvchilarga o'quvchilarning diqqatini jalb etish va darslarni jonlantirishda innovatsion vositalarni taklif qilmoqda. Interaktiv doskalar multimediya materiallari orqali turli o'quv uslublarini qamrab oluvchi darslarni tashkil qilish imkonini beradi. Maqolada texnologiyaning an'anaviy uslublar bilan uyg'unlashgan yondashuvi muhim ekani ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Interaktiv doska, raqamli ta'lim, o'quv uslublari, sinf xonasi, o'quvchilar, onlayn resurslar, ta'lim texnologiyalari, internet ulanishi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается применение технологий в обучении английскому языку, особенно использование интерактивных досок и онлайн-ресурсов. Технологии изменили традиционные методы преподавания, предлагая преподавателям

инновационные инструменты для повышения вовлеченности студентов. Интерактивные доски способствуют созданию мультимедийных и интерактивных уроков. В статье подчеркивается важность сбалансированного подхода, при котором технологии дополняют традиционные методы обучения.

Ключевые слова: Интерактивная доска, цифровое обучение, стили обучения, класс, студенты, онлайн-ресурсы, технологии в образовании, интернет-соединение.

INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly changing educational scene of today, technology has become an vital instrument for improving the quality of teaching and learning. Online resources and interactive whiteboards are particularly effective tools for teaching English among the many technology innovations. Dynamic, captivating lessons are offered with interactive whiteboards, which promote student involvement and enhance language learning. Additionally, online resources offer a wealth of materials, including videos, movies, games and interactive exercises, which cater to diverse learning styles. Teachers may establish a more engaging and productive learning environment that promotes improved language competence and communication skills by using these tools into their English language instruction. This paper explores the advantages of using resources in English language teaching , highlighting their impact on student engagement ,motivation and learning outcomes.

Interactive whiteboards are utilized in classrooms, conference rooms, hospitals, and other places where presentations are necessary. Using an interactive smart board, also referred to as an electronic whiteboard Hamdi , a digital projector can be used to display images from a computer screen on a school board [1] . The teacher or a student can engage with the visuals on the screen right away by using a tool or simply their finger. Using a computer connected to the internet or a local network, teachers can access resources from all over the world. They can look up a lesson they've already utilized with relative ease. Both teachers and students benefit from the classroom's interactive whiteboard. It invites the students to work together and engage more deeply in the lessons. The usage of multimedia materials in lectures can keep students interested. Using interactive whiteboards, different learning styles can be combined into a single experience. Through touch, auditory, and visual interactions with the board, students can learn. As a result, teachers are given innovative, unique approaches to teaching the same subject material. As a result, students learn more efficiently and retain more information. Students can participate in the curriculum by using interactive whiteboards. They take part in the lecture and are even able to teach one another. One can demonstrate their understanding of the material by touching, sketching, or writing on the board. Educational games can be played by the entire class.

Additionally, they provide prompt feedback so that instructors and students

can assess students development quickly. The interactive whiteboard is neat and easy to maintain. There is no requirement for chalk, markers, or any other writing implement. Data is annotated, written in, and highlighted using a socialized pen and therefore classroom instructions are presented without any clutter or cleanup. A variety of media formats can be shown on an interactive whiteboard. Teachers can create interesting lessons using a variety of tools at their disposal. Because of the internet connection built into the interactive whiteboard, a user has access to a wide range of online resources and data. To supplement and enhance their courses, teachers can use a wide range of resources, such as videos, articles, images, learning tools, and more.

Additionally, there are a ton of learning and research materials available to students. Thanks to interactive whiteboard technology, many new technologies can be integrated to enhance student learning.

CONCLUSIONS

According to the study, interactive whiteboards help students incorporate different learning methods into a single experience. They are also clean and extremely low maintenance, requiring no chalk, markers, or other writing implements. Teachers can supplement and complement their class with videos, articles, photos, learning tools, and more from a variety of sources. Students have access to a wealth of resources for learning and research. The surface of an interactive whiteboard can get scratched, it can be much more expensive than regular whiteboards or projection screens, and it can take up a lot of area in the classroom.

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ENHANCING FLIPPED CLASSROOMS WITH TELEGRAM: STRATEGIES, BENEFITS, AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: The flipped classroom model, which inverts traditional learning by having students engage with instructional materials at home and participate in interactive activities during class, has gained prominence in modern education. However, its success depends on effective digital tools that facilitate content delivery, communication, and engagement. This article explores the integration of **Telegram**, a cloud-based messaging platform, as a dynamic tool to enhance flipped learning. Through its features, such as **channels for content distribution, bots for automated quizzes, real-time polling, and file sharing**, Telegram supports all phases of flipped learning (pre-class, in-class, and post-class). The platform fosters **student engagement, self-paced learning, efficient communication, and collaboration**, while also addressing challenges such as accessibility, distractions, and privacy concerns. Drawing on existing research, this paper highlights Telegram's potential to bridge gaps in flipped classroom implementation, particularly in resource-constrained environments. The article concludes with recommendations for educators and suggests future research directions, including long-term impact studies and comparative analyses with other platforms.

Keywords: Flipped classroom, Telegram, Student engagement, Blended learning, Educational technology, Collaborative learning, Self-paced learning, Digital learning tools.

Аннотация: Модель перевернутого класса, которая инвертирует традиционное обучение, предлагая студентам изучать учебные материалы дома и участвовать в интерактивных занятиях в классе, приобрела значительную популярность в современном образовании. Однако ее успех зависит от эффективных цифровых инструментов, обеспечивающих доставку контента, коммуникацию и вовлеченность. В данной статье исследуется интеграция **Telegram**, облачной платформы для обмена сообщениями, в качестве динамичного инструмента для усиления перевернутого обучения. Благодаря таким функциям, как **каналы для распространения материалов, боты для автоматизированных тестов, опросы в реальном времени и обмен файлами**, Telegram поддерживает все этапы перевернутого обучения (до, во время и после занятия). Платформа способствует **вовлеченности студентов, самостоятельному обучению, эффективной коммуникации и сотрудничеству**, а также помогает решать проблемы, связанные с доступностью, отвлечением внимания и конфиденциальностью. Опираясь на существующие исследования, в статье подчеркивается потенциал Telegram для преодоления пробелов в реализации модели перевернутого класса, особенно в условиях ограниченных ресурсов. В заключение предлагаются рекомендации для преподавателей и направления для будущих исследований, включая изучение долгосрочного воздействия и сравнительный анализ с другими платформами.

Ключевые слова: Перевернутый класс, Telegram, Вовлеченность студентов, Смешанное обучение, Образовательные технологии, Коллаборативное обучение, Самостоятельное обучение, Цифровые инструменты обучения.

Annotatsiya: Flipped classroom – bu talabalarning uyda o'quv materiallari bilan shug'ullanishi va dars vaqtida interfaol mashg'ulotlarda qatnashishi orqali an'anaviy ta'lim jarayonini o'zgartiruvchi yondashuv bo'lib, zamonaviy ta'limda keng qo'llanilmoqda. Biroq, uning samaradorligi kontentni etkazish, kommunikatsiya va talabalarning jalb etilishini ta'minlaydigan samarali raqamli vositalarga bog'liq. Ushbu maqolada bulutli messaging platformasi bo'lgan **Telegramning** teskari ta'limni yaxshilash uchun dinamik vositasi sifatida integratsiyasi tadqiq qilinadi. Kontentni tarqatish kanallari, avtomatlashtirilgan testlar uchun botlar, real vaqt rejimida so'rovnomalar va fayl almashish kabi funksiyalari orqali Telegram teskari ta'limning barcha bosqichlarini (darsdan oldin, dars paytida va darsdan keyin) qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Platforma talabalarning jalb etilishi, individual ta'lim tezligi, samarali kommunikatsiya va hamkorlikni rag'batlantirish bilan birga, kirish imkoniyatlari, diqqatni chalg'itish va maxfiylik muammolarini hal qilishga yordam beradi. Mavjud tadqiqotlarga tayanib, ushbu maqola Telegramning, ayniqsa resurslar cheklangan muhitlarda, teskari sinf modelini joriy etishdagi bo'shliqlarni bartaraf etishdagi potensialini ta'kidlaydi. Maqola o'qituvchilar uchun tavsiyalar va uzoq muddatli ta'sirni o'rganish hamda boshqa platformalar bilan solishtirma tahlillarni o'z ichiga olgan kelajakdagi tadqiqot yo'nalishlari bilan yakunlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Teskari sinf modeli, Telegram, Talabalarning jalb etilishi, Aralash ta'lim, Ta'lim texnologiyalari, Hamkorlikdagi ta'lim, Individual ta'lim tezligi, Raqamli ta'lim vositalari.

The flipped classroom is an innovative pedagogical approach that reverses traditional learning structures. In this model, students review instructional materials—such as video lectures, readings, or multimedia content—independently at home, while class time is dedicated to interactive activities, discussions, and collaborative problem-solving (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). This shift empowers learners to engage deeply with content at their own pace while leveraging face-to-face sessions for higher-order thinking and application. However, the success of a flipped classroom hinges on effective pre-class engagement, necessitating digital tools that facilitate seamless content delivery, communication, and accountability. While platforms like Learning Management Systems (LMS) are widely used, they often lack the immediacy and interactivity that social messaging tools offer. Enter Telegram, a cloud-based messaging platform with features tailored for educational collaboration. Its channels, groups, bots, and file-sharing capabilities provide a dynamic space for distributing materials, fostering discussions, and automating feedback—making it an ideal companion for flipped learning. Telegram has emerged as a versatile tool for learning, particularly in the context of online education and distance learning. Its features, including channels and groups, bots, file sharing, and polling capabilities, facilitate engaging educational experiences. These functionalities offer significant advantages over other educational platforms.

Channels and Groups: Telegram channels and groups serve as effective platforms for content distribution and discussions among educators and learners. Channels allow teachers to disseminate learning materials broadly, while groups support discussion and collaboration among participants, fostering a community of

learning. Aghajani and Adloo highlight that such features contribute to enhancing students' attitudes towards learning by providing a medium where learners feel comfortable expressing themselves freely, thereby aiding their language development (Aghajani & Adloo, 2018). Similarly, Sarwari et al. note that the group chat feature supports interaction among students, thereby enriching the educational experience during remote learning periods (Sarwari et al., 2021).

Bots for Quizzes and Feedback: Telegram bots can automate quizzes and collect feedback, providing an interactive element to the learning process. These bots allow immediate assessment of students' understanding of course materials. Bakar et al. illustrate this by discussing how the Telegram Autobot Quiz can be utilized to improve spelling skills through engaging quizzes, showing the practical application of bots in language education (Bakar et al., 2019). The use of Telegram Chatbots facilitates constant interaction, contributing to a more effective educational environment by allowing constant access to learning materials and assistance (Ardimansyah & Widiyanto, 2021).

File Sharing and Resource Accessibility: Another significant advantage of Telegram is its capacity for file sharing, accommodating large media files without strict size limits. This characteristic ensures that students can access a variety of resources including videos and PDFs, crucial for pre-class preparation. Molina points out that Telegram provides more educational opportunities due to the diversity of its functionalities when compared to other platforms like WhatsApp, which may impose stricter limitations (Molina, 2022). Moreover, its resilience in low-internet conditions makes it particularly suitable for users in regions with limited connectivity (Rais et al., 2022).

Polling and Surveys for Instant Feedback: Telegram's polling feature enhances the educational experience by allowing teachers to gauge student understanding in real-time. Iqbal et al. emphasize that this feature can significantly supplement online medical education by quickly collecting opinions and feedback from students on various topics discussed during classes (Iqbal et al., 2020). Such tools provide instantaneous insights into student comprehension while also enhancing engagement by involving students in decision-making processes regarding their learning (Sarwari et al., 2021).

Privacy and Accessibility Advantages: Lastly, Telegram offers notable advantages in terms of privacy and accessibility, which are crucial in today's educational landscape. Unlike many popular social media platforms, Telegram prioritizes user privacy, allowing for confidential communications between students and educators. Furthermore, its cross-platform capabilities ensure that learners can access content at any time and place, thereby promoting flexible learning pathways. Iksan and Saufian underline the significant role Telegram plays in mobile learning,

thus supporting innovative teaching approaches amidst various challenges faced in traditional educational settings (Iksan & Saufian, 2017).

The integration of Telegram into flipped classroom methodologies can significantly enhance the learning experience across pre-class, in-class, and post-class phases. By leveraging the platform's features, educators can facilitate a more engaging and interactive environment for learners.

Pre-Class Phase: In the pre-class phase, Telegram serves as a vital tool for sharing lecture videos, reading materials, and quizzes. Teachers can utilize channels to distribute these resources efficiently, providing students with the necessary materials to prepare before class. This aligns with the flipped classroom model, where students engage with content at their own pace, absorbing knowledge independently before attending lectures (Guan, 2023). Additionally, quizzes via Telegram bots can promote active engagement, allowing for immediate feedback and understanding of the material (Ying & Ayub, 2022).

In-Class Phase: During class, Telegram can facilitate real-time polling, which encourages active participation and enables educators to gauge student understanding swiftly. This dynamic interaction allows the classroom to pivot towards collaborative tasks and peer feedback, enhancing the learning experience. As Bäcklund and Hugo noted, the flipped classroom model supports a shift in the educator's role from content delivery to facilitation of discussion and collaboration, promoting student-centered learning environments (Bäcklund & Hugo, 2018). Engaging students in real-time discussions helps create a more welcoming and interactive atmosphere that can improve learning outcomes (Fauzi, 2019). The real-time features of Telegram indeed encourage students to voice their thoughts and queries during class, enriching learning through collaborative dialogue (Pang, 2022).

Post-Class Phase: Following the class, Telegram supports reinforcement through continued discussions and resource sharing, which are crucial for knowledge retention and application. Educators can create post-class channels or groups to facilitate ongoing dialogue about the material covered, share additional resources, and solicit feedback from students about their learning experiences. This continuous engagement plays a vital role in solidifying concepts learned during class, consistent with research by Cheng et al., who found that post-class activities significantly impact student learning outcomes (Cheng et al., 2018). Furthermore, reinforcing learnings through such platforms promotes a sense of community among students, leading to higher engagement and self-efficacy (Jdaitawi, 2019).

The use of Telegram in the flipped classroom model not only enhances interactivity but also fosters a learner-centered environment that promotes autonomy and engagement. This tool provides educators with the flexibility to implement innovative teaching strategies that meet diverse learner needs, aligning with the

general principles of active learning methodologies emphasized in contemporary educational frameworks (Zhang, 2018).

Increased Student Engagement

Telegram's interactive features, including channels, groups, and bots, foster increased student engagement. The platform's mobile-friendly interface allows students to participate in discussions and access learning materials while on the go. As Chang et al. (2021) noted, the immediacy of interactions in mobile messaging applications like Telegram helps maintain students' interest in course content, thereby enhancing their overall learning experience. Moreover, interactive elements such as quizzes and polls stimulate student participation and drive engagement. Research indicates that interactive learning environments increase student motivation and involvement, essential components of effective flipped classrooms.

Efficient Communication

Telegram facilitates efficient communication between instructors and students through instant notifications and easy access to resources. Educators can deliver timely announcements, reminders, and updates, ensuring that all students receive relevant information simultaneously. Al-subhi et al. (2020) highlight that this efficient communication channel reduces the barriers to information flow and fosters a responsive educational atmosphere. The application's capability for quick responses to questions or concerns further enhances communication; students can seek clarification on materials shared prior to class, thereby promoting readiness and active participation.

Supports Self-Paced Learning

The asynchronous nature of flipped learning, enhanced by Telegram's functionalities, supports self-paced learning. Students can review materials, lecture videos, and resources at their own convenience, allowing them to take the time necessary to understand complex concepts thoroughly. Chen et al. (2017) emphasize that the ability to access learning materials at any time encourages students to engage with content more deeply and reinforces their understanding of subjects. This model allows students to tailor their learning experiences to fit their individual needs, which is particularly beneficial in a diverse educational landscape.

Encourages Collaboration

Telegram's group chat functionality encourages collaboration among students, fostering a sense of community and peer support. Students can engage in group discussions, exchange ideas, provide feedback, and collaborate on projects outside of formal classroom settings. The collaborative nature of Telegram aligns with the principles of constructivist learning, where knowledge construction occurs through social interactions. Research by Samah et al. (2020) supports the notion that platforms enabling collaborative learning through peer interactions significantly enhance student

engagement and performance outcomes. Furthermore, as noted by Muir (2019), platforms like Telegram create opportunities for peer support and encouragement, essential for student success in flipped learning environments.

Challenges and Considerations

While Telegram offers significant advantages for flipped classrooms, its implementation is not without challenges.

Distraction and Off-Topic Use

Telegram's social messaging nature may lead to **off-task behavior** if not properly moderated (Sarwari et al., 2021).

Educators must establish **clear guidelines** to maintain academic focus in group discussions.

Privacy and Data Security

While Telegram offers **end-to-end encryption**, educators must ensure compliance with **institutional data policies** (Iksan & Saufian, 2017).

Students' consent should be obtained before using third-party bots for assessments.

Conclusion and Future Directions

The integration of **Telegram in flipped classrooms** presents a promising avenue for **enhancing student engagement, communication, and self-paced learning**. Its features, such as **channels for content distribution, bots for automated quizzes, and real-time polling**, align well with the principles of flipped learning, fostering **active participation** both inside and outside the classroom. However, challenges such as the **digital divide, potential distractions, and teacher training** must be addressed to maximize its effectiveness. Future research should explore: **Long-term impacts** of Telegram-assisted flipped learning on academic performance. **Comparative studies** with other platforms (e.g., LMS, WhatsApp) to assess pedagogical efficiency.

As education continues to evolve in the digital age, **Telegram's flexibility and interactivity** position it as a valuable tool for **innovative teaching methodologies**. Educators are encouraged to **experiment with its features** while remaining mindful of its limitations to create **inclusive, engaging, and effective** flipped learning experiences.

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Peculiarities of Innovation Activities in Education: Contexts, Challenges, and Opportunities in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: Innovation in education has become vital for Uzbekistan's goal of transforming into a competitive knowledge-based economy. This paper explores the specific characteristics of innovation activities in education, with a focus on Uzbekistan. It analyzes drivers such as national reforms, digitalization, and global benchmarks, as well as barriers including infrastructure gaps, teacher preparedness, and systemic inertia. Drawing on local case studies and international best practices, the paper provides recommendations for sustainable and inclusive innovation in Uzbekistan's education sector.

Keywords: Educational innovation, Uzbekistan, teacher training, education reform, digital transformation, equity, pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekistonda ta'lim sohasida innovatsion faoliyatning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda, ayniqsa raqamlashtirish, xalqaro reytinglar va ta'lim sifatini oshirish maqsadida. Ushbu maqolada ta'limdagi innovatsiyalarni amalga oshirishning o'ziga xos jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, milliy islohotlar, texnologik yondashuvlar, pedagogik jarayonlardagi o'zgarishlar va ularni cheklovchi omillar (resurs yetishmasligi, o'qituvchilar tayyorgarligi) ko'rib chiqiladi. Mahalliy tajriba va xalqaro amaliyot asosida barqaror innovatsion strategiyalar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'limda innovatsiya, O'zbekiston, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, islohotlar, raqamli transformatsiya, tenglik, pedagogika.

Аннотация: Инновационная деятельность в системе образования Узбекистана приобретает все большее значение в контексте цифровизации, реформ и стремления к мировым стандартам. В статье рассматриваются особенности внедрения инноваций в образовательную сферу Узбекистана, включая движущие силы, такие как государственные программы, технологические изменения и потребности в квалифицированных кадрах. Также анализируются барьеры: недостаток инфраструктуры, подготовка педагогов и институциональные ограничения. Предлагаются рекомендации для устойчивого развития инноваций в образовании страны.

Ключевые слова: Инновации в образовании, Узбекистан, подготовка учителей, образовательная реформа, цифровизация, равенство, педагогика.

Education innovation in Uzbekistan is driven by sweeping national reforms and global partnership initiatives. Since 2017, the government's **Action Strategy** and Education Sector Plans (e.g. 2019–2023) have prioritized modernizing curricula, expanding access, and improving quality. Reforms restored grades 10–11 in schools, introduced presidential schools for talented youth, and raised teacher qualifications (over 80% of teachers now hold higher education). Uzbekistan's youth bulge – student enrollment grew by 7% (5.8→6.2 million from 2018–21) – has further underscored the need to innovate. Major policy changes (including a 2022 Presidential decree) set ambitious goals for quality and equity. With near-universal secondary enrollment ($\approx 99\%$) and substantial government spending on education ($\sim 5\text{--}6\%$ of GDP), the stage is set for transformative innovation. However, implementation gaps and legacy structures pose challenges that innovation must overcome.

Drivers of Innovation

National Reform Programs: Uzbekistan's reforms explicitly promote innovation. A new national curriculum emphasizes **critical thinking, problem-solving and practical skills**. The **Education Sector Plan 2019–23** and Vision 2030 strategy call for digitization and modern pedagogies. For example, the government launched an **ambitious digitalization program** – building online learning platforms and equipping schools with ICT – under “Digital Uzbekistan 2030”. Teacher quality is a priority: salaries have risen $\sim 50\%$ and training expanded. The ministry now retrain current teachers and recruits new ones to meet competency-based standards. International partnerships amplify these reforms: UNESCO, UNICEF and the World Bank provide technical support (e.g. new teacher-training projects) and investment. Notably, 2024 partnership compacts (GPE, World Bank) align government reforms with global best practices in curriculum, assessment, and data systems.

Digital and ICT Initiatives: Digital learning is a central innovation driver. UNESCO and UNICEF projects in Uzbekistan focus on *bridging the digital divide*. For instance, under a UNESCO/UNICEF “Empowering Education” project, educators are trained in UNESCO's ICT Competency Framework and AI-based tools. In 2025 Uzbekistan joined UNICEF's **Learning Pioneer** programme to pilot high-impact digital tools. As part of this, virtually **all schools** were connected (10 Mbps minimum) and equipped with computer labs. Pilot platforms like **Eduten** (a Finnish gamified AI math app) are being tested to complement teacher instruction. At the grassroots, initiatives like the national “*One Million Uzbek Programmers*” encourage ICT skills: teachers who complete digital training win prizes, and students have access to free coding courses and Udacity nanodegrees. Such efforts aim to create digitally-enabled classrooms and a STEM-skilled youth, reflecting a broader global trend of tech-rich education.

International Benchmarks and Best Practices: Uzbekistan draws on global

models. Presidential Schools for gifted secondary students (opened since 2019) exemplify this: curricula blend Cambridge A-level standards in STEM and English with national content, and teachers receive intensive professional development. Early results are promising (e.g. 68% of Presidential School students achieved A*-B in Cambridge A-levels, with all graduates earning tertiary placements). In pedagogy, UNESCO encourages *social-emotional learning (SEL)* and interactive methods; Uzbek teachers trained in SEL now integrate empathy and collaboration activities into lessons. Globally, UNESCO's "smart classroom" initiatives (e.g. in Pakistan) show technology can foster creativity and personalized learning. Uzbekistan's strategies reflect such best practices: curricula now highlight critical thinking, digital literacy and well-being. Participation in international assessments (PIRLS, TIMSS) also sets benchmarks, revealing learning gaps that guide improvement efforts.

Barriers to Innovation

Despite reforms, significant obstacles remain. **Infrastructure Gaps:** Many schools lack adequate facilities. Overcrowding is acute: more than 70% of Uzbek secondary schools still run **double shifts** to accommodate students, and class sizes often exceed the recommended 15:1 ratio. Much of the school stock dates from the Soviet era and lacks modern amenities. As one study notes, "basic features such as ramps, [accessible] toilets, ... and elevators are missing in most educational institutions, particularly in rural ... regions". Even beyond physical accessibility, ICT infrastructure lags; rural schools struggle with connectivity and lack devices. These conditions hinder introducing innovative teaching methods or tech-driven learning.

Teacher Preparedness: Uzbek teachers often lack training for new pedagogies and technologies. A World Bank analysis bluntly cites "low teacher quality" as a key cause of poor student outcomes. Universities rarely select or prepare aspiring teachers for modern demands: "the curriculum of preservice [programs] is outdated...[it] does not foster a student-centered approach or 21st-century skills". In-service training is often piecemeal. Many educators are unfamiliar with differentiated instruction, ICT tools or SEL methods. For example, UNESCO found that without targeted training, teachers struggle to integrate digital tools or adapt to inclusive classrooms. The recruitment system adds to the problem: hiring remains decentralized and opaque, and many graduates enter teaching "as a last resort". Ultimately, innovation falters if teachers lack skills or incentives to implement it.

Systemic Inertia: Institutional barriers slow change. Uzbekistan's new policies sometimes exist more on paper than in practice. A study of inclusive education notes that despite progressive laws (e.g. Education Law 2020), actual implementation is uneven: "operational guidelines... are inconsistent and uneven across regions," and accountability mechanisms are weak. Siloed management (e.g. separate ministries for education, health, etc.) and limited budgets mean reforms stall at local levels. Similarly,

traditional attitudes and rigid centralized practices persist. Curricula and exams remain largely exam-driven, leaving little room for creativity or student-centered methods. Social expectations and stigma (especially around disability) also inhibit novel practices. In short, even bold initiatives like “new curriculum” or “digital classrooms” face slow uptake when bureaucratic routines and legacy culture are not fully aligned.

Local Case Studies and Initiatives

Several Uzbek innovations illustrate these dynamics. The **Presidential Schools** (specialized boarding schools) showcase curriculum and teaching innovation: they recruit gifted 11–18-year-olds nationwide, focus heavily on STEM, languages and leadership skills, and adopt international standards in teaching and assessment. For example, their curriculum was co-designed with Cambridge University Press, and teachers receive intensive professional development. Early outcomes are high: in 2022 all Presidential School graduates earned university offers (30% to overseas institutions).

Another example is the “**One Million Uzbek Programmers**” initiative. Co-launched in 2019 by the Ministries of Education and ICT (and Dubai Future Foundation), it created a free online coding platform (UzbekCoders.uz) offering courses in programming, and awarded Udacity nanodegree opportunities to completersuzedu.uz. By 2022 the government hosted national contests and prizes for the most engaged schools and teachers in the programme. This project not only builds IT skills among youth, but, as UNESCO reports, “*incentivizes teachers to use digital tools by offering prizes for completing digital education training*”. Such schemes connect everyday instruction to international tech ecosystems (Udacity certificates are recognized by companies like Google and Autodeskuzedu.uz).

UN agency-supported pilots also illustrate innovation. The UNICEF/UNESCO **Eduten** pilot in 2023 brought an AI-driven math app (used in 50 countries) into Uzbek schools to complement teacher-led math classes. Educators in target regions received digital math training and used tablets in class. Early feedback indicates higher student engagement. Similarly, the “Empowering Education” project led by UNESCO (with UNICEF support) dispatched ICT specialists (e.g. Wendy Gorton) to rural teacher-training centers in 2025 to establish ICT competency frameworks and train master trainers. These efforts are documented successes: in one mission, digital teacher training modules and AI-based tools were co-developed with local educators, explicitly aiming to “*ensure no teacher or student is left behind in the digital era*”.

International Best Practices

Uzbekistan’s innovators can also learn from global peers. For example, **Pakistan’s smart classrooms** project (UNESCO-supported) installed modern lab equipment and interactive content in 40 schools, observing that “*access to modern technology and interactive learning resources*” significantly boosts creativity and

learning among girls. Latin American countries (e.g. Uruguay's Plan Ceibal) have shown how one-to-one laptop distribution can close learning gaps. High-performing systems like Singapore continuously revise curricula to embed holistic competencies and digital literacy. These models suggest Uzbekistan should continue integrating technology with pedagogical reform, ensure equity (so rural and disabled students gain access), and invest in teacher communities of practice. Additionally, regional neighbors offer lessons: for instance, **Kyrgyzstan** automated teacher certification and provided large-scale in-service training, which Uzbekistan could emulate to upgrade its profession.

Recommendations for Sustainable, Inclusive Innovation

To build on these efforts, Uzbekistan should pursue a multifaceted strategy:

- **Upgrade Infrastructure and Connectivity.** Continue expanding high-speed internet and devices nationwide; retrofit older schools for accessibility. (UNICEF's mapping shows nearly all schools now have 10 Mbps connectivity.) Invest in reducing double-shifts by building new schools and equipping them with ICT labs.

- **Enhance Teacher Capacity and Incentives.** Strengthen pre-service and in-service training so teachers master 21st-century pedagogy (including SEL and tech use). Systematically implement the new ICT competency framework. Introduce regular professional development (e.g. EdTech workshops) and career paths. Reform hiring and certification (as in Kyrgyzstan) to select and reward high-performing educators.

- **Leverage Digital Learning Platforms.** Scale successful pilots like the Eduten math platform to other subjects. Develop local e-content in Uzbek and integrate AI-driven tools in classrooms. Use data from these platforms to track student progress (addressing the World Bank's call for better data systems).

- **Align Policy and Accountability.** Strengthen policy implementation by issuing clear guidelines and coordinating ministries (as critics have noted). Establish monitoring frameworks with measurable indicators (inclusion, outcomes, tech use) and empower local leaders to innovate under these guidelines.

- **Promote Inclusive and Student-Centered Practices.** Reform exam and assessment systems to value critical thinking and creativity. Incorporate smaller class sizes and flexible timetabling. Continue the inclusive education campaign: equip more schools with ramps and assistive tech, and train teachers in differentiated instruction. Involve communities to change attitudes and support learners of all backgrounds.

- **Foster Partnerships and Funding.** Maintain and expand partnerships with international institutions (UNESCO, World Bank, foreign universities) and private sector (e.g. ICT companies) to share resources and expertise. Explore innovative financing (e.g. education endowments or social impact bonds) to sustain programs. Ensure that education budget allocations target innovation (consistent with UNESCO's emphasis on sustained funding).

Each recommendation is informed by experience: for instance, digital platforms in math have improved engagement, and focused teacher training in SEL and technology has yielded more interactive classrooms. By systematically addressing infrastructure, pedagogy, policy, and inclusivity, Uzbekistan can create a self-sustaining innovation ecosystem in its secondary education system.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan stands at a pivotal moment: rapid reforms and international support have created an unprecedented opportunity to transform secondary education. A combination of national vision (curriculum overhaul, digitalization, teacher investment) and grassroots innovation (teacher-led tech initiatives, specialized schools) is underway. However, realizing the full promise of innovation requires concerted effort to overcome concrete barriers (infrastructure deficits, skill gaps, and systemic inertia). Drawing on both local successes and global models, Uzbekistan can pursue a comprehensive strategy – one that modernizes learning environments, empowers educators, and keeps equity at the center. Such an approach will not only improve test scores, but also foster the creativity, critical thinking and lifelong learning skills that students need in the 21st century.

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SONGS IN THE ESL CLASSROOM: A METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article explores the methodological use of songs in English as a Second Language (ESL) classes. It highlights the cognitive and emotional benefits of music, the enhancement of language skills, and practical classroom strategies for implementation.

Keywords: songs, ESL, language acquisition, music in education, student engagement.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rgatishda qo'shiq va musiqalardan metodik foydalanish masalasini ko'rib chiqadi. Unda musiqaning ta'limiy va hissiy afzalliklari, til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi roli hamda amaliy o'quv yondashuvlari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'shiqlar, ESL, til o'zlashtirish, ta'limda musiqa, talabalar faolligi.

Аннотация: Данная статья рассматривает методическое использование песен на уроках английского как второго языка. Рассматриваются когнитивные и эмоциональные преимущества музыки, развитие языковых навыков и практические стратегии преподавания.

Ключевые слова: песни, ESL, усвоение языка, музыка в образовании, вовлеченность студентов.

Introduction

In the evolving landscape of English as a Second Language (ESL) education, teachers are continually seeking innovative methods to engage learners and improve language acquisition. Among these methods, the use of songs has emerged as an effective and enjoyable tool in the language classroom. Songs combine rhythm, melody, and meaningful language, making them ideal for reinforcing vocabulary, improving listening comprehension, and fostering cultural awareness. This article examines the methodological role of songs in ESL classrooms and explores their effects on learners' linguistic and emotional engagement.

Theoretical Background

Music and language share a deep neurological connection, which explains why songs can be an effective tool for teaching English as a Second Language (ESL). Research shows that both language syntax and music patterns are processed in the same region of the brain—Broca's area (Maess et al., 2001). This discovery highlights the pattern-making similarity between language and music. Additionally, emotional reactions to music engage the limbic system, a part of the brain associated with strong emotional learning (Moreno, 2008). Because music stimulates multiple brain areas simultaneously, it creates an ideal environment for attention and memory, two critical components of language acquisition. According to Lems (2018), when learners

experience heightened attention through musical activities, their ability to absorb and retain new information increases. Thus, integrating songs into ESL classrooms is not merely a motivational tool; it is a method grounded in cognitive science and brain-based learning theories.

Benefits of Using Songs in ESL Classes

Using songs in ESL classrooms offers a wide range of benefits that go beyond simple entertainment. Research shows that music can lower the affective filter—a mental block that prevents students from absorbing language input due to anxiety, stress, or lack of confidence (Talada, 2015). When learners are more relaxed and motivated, they engage more deeply with the material and retain it better. Songs also provide rich linguistic input, offering opportunities for vocabulary development, pronunciation practice, and the reinforcement of grammar structures (Lems, 2018). Kristin Lems (2018) further explains that songs activate Broca's area, Wernicke's area, and the limbic system, combining pattern recognition, language processing, and emotional memory. This deep cognitive activation explains why songs are so effective at creating lasting language memories. Additionally, using songs can boost students' self-confidence by allowing them to participate in less formal, lower-pressure activities where mistakes are less emphasized. Talada's (2015) study confirmed that students reported higher levels of motivation, self-confidence, and perceived proficiency after participating in music-based tasks. Therefore, songs serve not only as linguistic input but also as emotional and motivational support tools in ESL learning.

Practical Implementation of Songs in ESL Classes

Incorporating songs into ESL classrooms can be highly effective when approached with clear pedagogical strategies. Lems (2018) proposes several practical techniques, such as using songs for listening comprehension through transcription activities, promoting speaking through student presentations about favorite music, and enhancing vocabulary through lyric analysis. Dividing students into groups to transcribe a song verse-by-verse, for example, strengthens listening skills and fosters collaborative learning. Reading comprehension can also be improved by using song lyrics as texts for inferential reading tasks, encouraging students to make connections and deepen understanding. Talada (2015) emphasizes the importance of careful song selection to ensure that the content aligns with linguistic goals and student interests, minimizing challenges like slang, fast tempos, or culturally unfamiliar references. Moreover, songs can be integrated to promote writing skills by inviting students to create poems, journal entries, or creative responses inspired by instrumental music. Such activities make language learning multi-sensory and emotionally resonant. To maximize the effectiveness of songs in teaching, instructors should select appropriate materials, scaffold activities carefully, and be sensitive to student comfort levels, particularly when asking them to sing or perform. Through thoughtful integration,

songs can transform ESL classrooms into vibrant, motivating, and language-rich environments.

Conclusion

The integration of songs into ESL classrooms offers more than just an enjoyable break from traditional instruction; it serves as a powerful methodological tool that enhances language acquisition. As the research shows, songs engage multiple areas of the brain responsible for pattern recognition, emotional memory, and language processing, creating an ideal environment for learning (Lems, 2018). Music-based instruction not only supports vocabulary development, listening comprehension, and pronunciation, but also lowers the affective filter, thereby boosting student motivation, self-confidence, and overall engagement with the language (Talada, 2015). Practical activities such as lyric transcription, inferential reading, and creative writing through music further demonstrate how songs can be effectively integrated into teaching practices to promote both linguistic and emotional growth. By thoughtfully selecting appropriate musical materials and designing targeted activities, educators can unlock the full potential of songs as an essential part of language learning. Ultimately, incorporating music into ESL instruction transforms the classroom into a dynamic, inclusive, and emotionally supportive space where students can thrive.

Suggestions and Recommendations:

- Teachers should select songs that are level-appropriate and culturally relevant.
- It is recommended to use pre-listening and post-listening tasks to support comprehension.
- Song-based activities should be varied and integrated into all four language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.
- Further research could explore the long-term effects of song integration on student motivation and retention.

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The Impact of Using Technology in Teaching English as a Foreign Language

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Abstract: In recent decades, the integration of technology into education has transformed the way languages are taught and learned. Specifically, in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), technological tools and platforms have redefined the traditional classroom, offering dynamic and interactive ways to develop learners' linguistic skills. Technology exposes learners to authentic English through podcasts, news, social media, and real-time conversations. This prepares them for practical, real-life communication beyond the classroom. Through video chats, forums, and global collaborations, students practice English with peers worldwide. This not only improves fluency but also enhances intercultural competence.

Key words: interaction, dynamic, enhance, transform, digital, competence, advanced, expose, collaboration, content, engage, access, ownership, relatable.

Аннотация: В последние десятилетия интеграция технологий в образование изменила способ преподавания и изучения языков. В частности, в области английского языка как иностранного (EFL) технологические инструменты и платформы изменили традиционный класс, предлагая динамичные и интерактивные способы развития языковых навыков учащихся. Технологии знакомят учащихся с аутентичным английским языком через подкасты, новости, социальные сети и разговоры в реальном времени. Это готовит их к практическому, реальному общению за пределами класса. С помощью видеочатов, форумов и глобального сотрудничества студенты практикуют английский язык со сверстниками по всему миру. Это не только улучшает беглость, но и повышает межкультурную компетентность.

Ключевые слова: взаимодействие, динамичный, улучшать, преобразовывать, цифровой, компетентность, продвинутый, раскрывать, сотрудничество, контент, вовлекать, доступ, владение, соотносимый.

Annotatsiya: So'nggi o'n yilliklarda texnologiyaning ta'limga integratsiyalashuvi tillarni o'rgatish va o'rganish usullarini o'zgartirdi. Xususan, ingliz tili chet tili (EFL) sohasida texnologik vositalar va platformalar talabalarning til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning dinamik va interaktiv usullarini taklif qilib, an'anaviy sinfni o'zgartirdi. Texnologiya podkastlar, yangiliklar, ijtimoiy media va real vaqtda suhbatlar orqali talabalarni asl ingliz tili bilan tanishtiradi. Bu ularni sinfdan tashqarida amaliy, real hayotdagi muloqotga tayyorlaydi. Video suhbatlar, forumlar va global hamkorlik orqali talabalar butun dunyodagi tengdoshlari bilan ingliz tilini mashq qiladilar. Bu nafaqat ravonlikni yaxshilaydi, balki madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyani ham oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zaro ta'sir, dinamik, takomillashtirish, o'zgartirish, raqamli, kompetentsiya, rivojlangan, oshkor qilish, hamkorlik, kontent, jalb qilish.

Learning English is important because it is the most widely spoken and used language in the world for communication, education, business, and travel. As the global language of science, technology, and the internet, English connects people across cultures and countries, opening doors to international opportunities and information. For students and professionals alike, proficiency in English enhances access to quality

education, competitive jobs, and global networks. It also helps individuals participate more fully in a rapidly globalizing world, where English often serves as a common ground for interaction and collaboration.

In today's quickly advancing instructive scene, innovation has gotten to be a crucial apparatus within the educating of English as a foreign language (EFL). The integration of digital tools, platforms, and resources has transformed traditional classrooms into dynamic, interactive learning environments. This shift not only enhances language acquisition but also bridges cultural and communicative gaps, making English learning more accessible and engaging for students across the globe. One of the most significant impacts of technology in EFL classrooms is its ability to increase student engagement. Interactive tools such as language learning apps (e.g., Duolingo, Memrise), online games, and multimedia content make learning English fun and relatable. These resources provide instant feedback and a sense of achievement, which motivate learners to persist in their studies. Moreover, gamification—using elements of game design in educational contexts - encourages students to actively participate and take ownership of their learning.

Technology allows for a more personalized approach to language instruction. Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle or Google Classroom enable teachers to design custom lessons, track progress, and provide targeted feedback based on individual student needs. Adaptive learning technologies can assess a learner's proficiency level and tailor exercises to strengthen weaker areas, making the learning process more efficient and student-centered. Technology breaks down geographical and temporal barriers in language education. Through online courses, virtual classrooms, and video conferencing tools like Zoom and Skype, learners can access high-quality English instruction from anywhere in the world. This accessibility is especially beneficial for students in remote or underserved areas. It also supports asynchronous learning, allowing learners to study at their own pace and according to their schedules.

Moreover, the use of technology facilitates authentic communication with native speakers and other learners worldwide through language exchange websites, discussion forums, and social media. These interactions promote cultural awareness and encourage the practical use of English in diverse contexts. Such exposure is crucial for developing fluency and confidence in using the language beyond the confines of the classroom.

Despite its benefits, the use of technology in EFL teaching is not without challenges. Issues such as limited access to devices or the internet, lack of digital literacy among educators, and the risk of over-reliance on technology must be addressed. Effective implementation requires teacher training, careful planning, and the integration of technology as a complement - not a replacement - for pedagogical

best practices.

Technology has revolutionized the way English is taught and learned in the modern era. It provides learners with tools for independent study, immersive practice, and real-time feedback while empowering teachers to deliver more effective and engaging instruction. As digital innovation continues to evolve, its role in English language learning will only grow more significant — shaping a future where mastering English is more attainable, personalized, and global than ever before. While technology alone cannot replace the value of human interaction and the role of skilled educators, it serves as a powerful complement to traditional English language learning. Its role is not just to digitize old methods but to redefine how language is practiced, applied, and experienced. As artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and machine learning continue to develop, the future holds even more immersive and intelligent language-learning environments. To fully harness these benefits, both learners and educators must adapt by developing digital literacy and staying open to innovation. Ultimately, the thoughtful integration of technology promises not only more efficient language acquisition but also a more inclusive and interconnected global learning community.

Learning English through technology is highly effective due to its ability to provide interactive, flexible, and personalized learning experiences. Digital tools such as language apps, online courses, and AI-powered platforms offer learners instant feedback, authentic content, and opportunities for real-time communication with native speakers. These tools enhance motivation, support self-paced learning, and cater to different learning styles. While technology cannot fully replace human instruction, when used effectively, it significantly improves language skills, especially in listening, speaking, reading, and writing, making it a powerful aid in modern English language education.

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TIL VA MADANIYAT: INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR UYG'UNLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Global miqyosda chet tillarni o'qitishda madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasining yetishmasligi o'quvchilarning til o'zlashtirish jarayonida muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Bu holat, ayniqsa, raqamli muhitda madaniy tafovutlar va noto'g'ri tushunishlar sababli muloqotning uzilishi, stereotiplar va madaniy qarama-qarshiliklarga olib kelmoqda. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qituvchilarning madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasini oshirish orqali bu muammolarni bartaraf etish mumkin.

Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi muammolar va ularni hal etish yo'llari, jumladan, translanguaging, virtual almashinuv va kod-meshing kabi innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali o'quvchilarda global tafakkurni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatlararo muloqot, global tafakkur, til o'qitish metodikasi, innovatsion yondashuvlar, raqamli muhit.

Annotation: Globally, the lack of intercultural communication competence in foreign language education leads to challenges in language acquisition. In digital environments, cultural misunderstandings and communication breakdowns often result from these deficiencies. Research indicates that enhancing teachers' intercultural competence can address these issues effectively. This article examines the problems in intercultural communication and explores solutions such as translanguaging, virtual exchanges, and code-meshing. These innovative approaches aim to foster global thinking among learners.

Keywords: Intercultural communication, global thinking, language teaching methodology, innovative approaches, digital environment.

Аннотация: На глобальном уровне недостаток межкультурной коммуникативной компетенции в обучении иностранным языкам приводит к трудностям в освоении языка. В цифровой среде культурные недопонимания и сбои в коммуникации часто являются следствием этих недостатков. Исследования показывают, что повышение межкультурной компетенции преподавателей может эффективно решить эти проблемы.

В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы межкультурной коммуникации и предлагаются решения, такие как транслангвизм, виртуальные обмены и код-мешинг. Эти инновационные подходы направлены на формирование глобального мышления у учащихся

Ключевые слова: Межкультурная коммуникация, глобальное мышление, методика преподавания языка, инновационные подходы, цифровая среда.

KIRISH

Bugungi globallashuv jarayoni har bir insonni nafaqat o'z jamiyatida, balki butun dunyo miqyosida fikr yuritishga, muloqot qilishga va madaniy tafovutlarni to'g'ri anglashga majbur qilmoqda. Ayniqsa, xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayoni endi oddiy lug'at yodlash va grammatikani o'zlashtirishdan iborat bo'lmay, balki xalqaro hamkorlik, madaniyatlararo aloqalar va global tafakkurni shakllantirish vositasiga aylanmoqda.

Shu o'rinda bir global muammoni ta'kidlash joiz: til o'qitish tizimi ko'plab hududlarda hali ham an'anaviy, passiv va hayotdan uzilgan metodlarga tayanmoqda. Bu esa o'quvchilarning chet tilini faqat sinfda, nazariy darajada o'rganishiga, ammo real hayotda qo'llay olmasligiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Men shaxsan ishonamanki, bu muammoni yechishning eng asosiy yo'li — innovatsion metodlar va raqamli texnologiyalar asosida faol, muloqotga yo'naltirilgan o'qituv tizimlarini joriy etishdir. So'nggi yillarda chop etilayotgan ilmiy ishlar bazasida e'lon qilingan ko'plab ilmiy maqolalar bu fikrni tasdiqlaydi: masalan, García & Wei (2014) translanguaging orqali o'quvchilar ongida til va madaniyat chegaralarini yo'q qilish mumkinligini ko'rsatgan bo'lsa, O'Dowd (2018) esa virtual almashinuv tajribalari orqali til o'rganishni global ijtimoiy kontekstga olib chiqish mumkinligini ilmiy isbotlagan.

Ushbu maqolada men chet tilini o'qitishda translanguaging, kod-meshing, virtual almashinuv, va boshqa interaktiv metodlarning madaniyatlararo muloqot va global tafakkur shakllanishiga ta'siri haqida shaxsiy fikrlarim va tahlillarimni bo'lishamam.

Innovatsion til o'rgatish uslublariga shaxsiy yondashuv: Translanguaging, kod-meshing va virtual almashinuvning amaliy qiymati.

Til o'rganish jarayonida oddiy grammatik yondashuvdan ko'ra, hayotiy va madaniy kontekstga tayangan metodlarni doim samarali yechim sifatida ko'rganman. Aynan shunday **usullardan biri** — translanguaging. Bu metod orqali o'quvchi o'z ona tilini chet tilini tushunishda ko'priq sifatida ishlatadi. Menimcha, bu nafaqat o'rganishni osonlashtiradi, balki o'zlikni inkor qilmasdan, boshqa tilni qabul qilishni ta'minlaydi. Bu metod bo'yicha García va Wei (2014) translanguaging nafaqat til, balki madaniy va tafakkur doirasida ham erkinlik beradi, deb ta'kidlaydi — va men bu fikrni shaxsan o'z tajribamdan kelib chiqib tasdiqlay olaman. **Ikkinchi usul** — kod-meshing — o'quvchiga tilni real hayotda aralashtirib ishlatishga ruxsat beradi. Men darslarda ba'zida o'zbekcha fikrni ingliz tilidagi jumlag qo'shib, tabiiy tarzda ifoda qilganimda, o'z fikrimni yanada aniqroq va erkinroq bayon qilganimni sezaman. Canagarajah (2013) bu holatni ijobiy baholab, kod-meshing til o'rganuvchining

ovozini (voice) kuchaytiradi, deydi. Shaxsan men bu usul o'quvchining o'zini ifoda etishdagi ishonchini oshiradi deb hisoblayman.

Uchinchi muhim metod — virtual almashinuv (Virtual Exchange). Men xalqaro forumlar va til o'rganishga yo'naltirilgan onlayn loyihalarda qatnashganimda, ingliz tilini faqat lug'at va grammatik qoidalar asosida emas, balki real muloqot vositasi sifatida o'rganishga majbur bo'lganman. Bu esa tilni o'rganishga bo'lgan munosabatimni tubdan o'zgartirdi. O'Dowd (2018) yozganidek, virtual almashinuv o'quvchilarni madaniyatlararo kontekstda mustaqil fikrlashga o'rgatadi — va bu haqiqat.

Bu uch metod menga nafaqat tilni o'rganishda, balki o'z fikrimni ravon, tushunarli va madaniyatlararo kontekstda ifoda etishda katta yordam berdi. Shu sababli, men bu yondashuvlarni nafaqat zamonaviy, balki ehtiyojga eng mos keladigan innovatsiyalar deb bilaman.

Madaniyatlararo aloqalar va til: O'zaro bog'liq jarayon sifatida innovatsion yondashuvlar

Men uchun tilni o'rganish hech qachon faqat grammatikani bilish yoki so'z boyligini oshirish emas. Til — bu madaniyatning ko'zgusi, jamiyatning ruhi. Shu sababli, chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida madaniyatlararo tafakkurga ega bo'lish mening eng muhim tamoyillarimdan biriga aylangan. Tilni o'zlashtirishning o'zi yetarli emas — samarali muloqot uchun madaniyatlararo tushuncha ham zarur — quloq eshitganini tushunishi, ammo yurak bilan anglay olmasligi mumkin. Chunki har bir so'z, ibora va jumla o'ziga xos kontekstga ega bo'ladi. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi "How are you?" oddiy so'rash emas, balki jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy mehr va e'tiborning ifodasidir. Men shuni anglaganimdan so'ng, til o'rganishga munosabatim butkul o'zgardi.

Elsevier nashriyotidagi so'nggi izlanishlarda ham bu yondashuv keng yoritilgan. Risager (2021) o'z tadqiqotida madaniyatlararo yondashuvni til o'rgatishda asosiy tamoyil sifatida ko'rsatgan va bu fikrga men ham qo'shilaman. Ayniqsa, onlayn platformalarda dunyoning turli burchaklaridagi insonlar bilan muloqot qilish orqali men turli millat vakillarining dunyoqarashi, qadriyati va muloqot madaniyatini o'rganish imkoniga ega bo'ldim.

Innovatsion metodlardan biri — madaniy simulyatsiya (cultural simulation) — men uchun haqiqiy ochilish bo'ldi. Talabalar yoki o'rganuvchilar turli madaniy holatlarni rolli o'yin shaklida bajarar ekan, nafaqat tilni, balki boshqa madaniyatni ham "ichidan" his qiladi. Bu usul orqali men o'zbekona muloyimlikni ingliz tilida qanday ifoda etish mumkinligini real mashqlarda sinab ko'rdim.

Bundan tashqari, raqamli madaniyatlararo almashinuv platformalari — masalan, **eTandem**, **GlobalClassroom**, **TalkAbroad** — men uchun tilni tirik va dolzarb qilishda ayni muddao bo'ldi. Bu vositalar orqali men ingliz tilini real, global va madaniy kontekstda qo'llashga odatlandim. O'Dowd (2020) shunday

platformalarning madaniyatlararo salohiyatini keng tahlil qilib, ularni “digital cultural bridges” deb atagan — va men bunga o‘z hayotimdagi jonli misollarga tayangan holda uning fikrlarini qo‘llab quvvatlayman.

Shu asosda aytishim mumkinki, til va madaniyatni bir-biridan ajratmaslik kerak. Ularga integrativ yondashuvigina haqiqiy kommunikativ salohiyatni beradi. Bu esa, nafaqat yaxshi tarjima yoki grammatik aniqlik, balki haqiqiy xalqaro tushunish, muloqot va hamkorlikni kafolatlaydi.

XULOSA

Chet tillarini o‘qitish bugungi global dunyoda faqat til ko‘nikmalarini emas, balki xalqaro muloqot, madaniy empatiya va tushunishni shakllantiruvchi vositaga aylanishi zarur. Men o‘z tajribam orqali tilni o‘rganish — bu bir vaqtning o‘zida boshqa madaniyatni tushunish, o‘zimni yangi ijtimoiy kontekstlarda his qilish va o‘rganilgan til orqali fikr almashish imkoniyatini topish ekanligini angladim.

Shu asosda, innovatsion usullar — xususan, translanguaging, madaniy simulyatsiyalar, virtual almashinuv platformalari, va kod-meshing kabi yondashuvlar — tilni faqat nazariy emas, balki real hayotga bog‘lab o‘rganishga yordam beradi. Bu yondashuvlar orqali men tilni insoniy qadriyatlar, ijtimoiy muloqot va madaniy xilma-xillik doirasida o‘zlashtirish imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ldim.

Shunday ekan, til va madaniyatni ajratib bo‘lmaydi. Til — bu madaniyatning “tovushi”, madaniyat esa tilning “ma’nosi”dir. Har bir o‘quvchi yoki o‘rganuvchi aynan shu uyg‘unlikni his etgan holda o‘z til o‘rganish yo‘lini boshlasa, natijalar nafaqat lingvistik, balki insoniy, global va ijtimoiy darajada ham yuksak bo‘ladi.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING INNOVATIONS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: This article examines the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the language teaching system and their role in the formation of intercultural communication. Also, the integration of the multimodal approach, digital tools, and the cultural component in the development of communicative competence in the process of teaching foreign languages is analyzed. The article, based on international experience and scientific literature, reveals the theoretical and practical significance of innovations in language teaching and the development of intercultural competence.

Keywords: intercultural communication, innovative technologies, communicative competence, digital education.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается внедрение современных инновационных технологий в систему обучения языкам и их роль в формировании межкультурной коммуникации. Также анализируется интеграция мультимодального подхода, цифровых инструментов и культурной составляющей в развитии коммуникативной компетенции в процессе обучения иностранным языкам. В статье на основе международного опыта и научной литературы раскрывается теоретическая и практическая значимость инноваций в обучении языкам и развитии межкультурной компетенции.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная коммуникация, инновационные технологии, коммуникативная компетентность, цифровое образование.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til o'qitish tizimiga zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish va ularning madaniyatlararo muloqotni shakllantirishdagi o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi. Chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda multimodal yondashuv, raqamli vositalar va madaniy komponentlarning integratsiyasi ham tahlil qilinadi. Xalqaro tajriba va ilmiy adabiyotlarga asoslangan maqolada til o'rgatish va madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirishdagi innovatsiyalarning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, innovatsion texnologiyalar, kommunikativ kompetensiya, raqamli ta'lim.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, learning a foreign language has become a necessity not only for satisfying communicative needs, but also for effective integration into international cultural communication. It is observed that modern language teaching methodology is transitioning from traditional grammar-reading approaches to modern, interactive, communicative, and multimodal platforms. In this case, along with the deepening of students' language competence, the development of their

intercultural sensitivity is of great importance (Byram, 1997).

In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. Due to the fact that specialists in various fields have a high level of cooperation with foreign partners, they have a high demand for language learning. Currently, foreign languages are taught in schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher educational institutions. There are innovative types of educational materials for those who want to have different levels of language proficiency.

MAIN PART

In the era of globalization, the role of foreign language education and intercultural communication has become increasingly vital. As linguistic competence is now inseparable from cultural competence, modern teaching practices must go beyond traditional methods to meet the needs of 21st-century learners. The application of innovative approaches—such as digital learning platforms, artificial intelligence, immersive technologies (e.g., virtual and augmented reality), and gamification—not only enhances language acquisition but also fosters a deeper understanding of cultural diversity.

Innovations in foreign language teaching allow educators to tailor instruction to individual learning styles, promote learner autonomy, and facilitate real-time interaction with native speakers around the world. For instance, mobile applications, online exchange programs, and AI-powered chatbots provide learners with authentic contexts for practicing language and understanding cultural nuances. Furthermore, the integration of project-based learning, CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), and the STEAM approach ensures that students develop both linguistic and critical thinking skills while engaging with global issues.

Intercultural communication, a key component of language learning, benefits immensely from innovative methodologies that emphasize empathy, cultural awareness, and global citizenship. Virtual cultural exchanges and digital storytelling help dismantle stereotypes and encourage inclusive attitudes, which are essential for effective communication in multicultural environments.

In conclusion, the application of innovation in language education not only accelerates language mastery but also prepares learners to function successfully in a multicultural, interconnected world. To remain relevant and effective, foreign language teaching must continue to evolve through the strategic integration of technology and culturally responsive pedagogy.

1. Innovative technologies and the transformation of language teaching

Digital technologies have ushered in a new era in language teaching. With the help of online platforms (Duolingo, Quizlet, Moodle), artificial intelligence-based programs (ChatGPT, Grammarly), gamification (kahoot, classcraft) and AR/VR technologies, the language learning process is becoming more interactive and

individualized. For example, as Laurillard (2012) noted, digital pedagogical models serve to form a reflective, constructive and active approach to language teaching.

Through innovative technologies, the student:

- receives multi-channel (audio-visual-kinesthetic) education;
- has the opportunity to “immerse” in the language environment in real time;
- strives to understand the cultural context.

2. Integration of intercultural dialogue and language teaching

Language is not only a means of communication, but also a social phenomenon that carries culture. Learning a foreign language requires effective intercultural communication. Byram (1997) defines intercultural competence as consisting of the following components:

- socio-cultural knowledge;
- intercultural interpretation and relational skills;
- tolerance and openness.

To develop these components, approaches such as CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), task-based learning (TBL), and authentic materials (materials with real cultural context) are used to increase effectiveness (Coyle, Hood & Marsh, 2010).

3. Developing intercultural competence through innovative approaches

The following innovative methods have been effective in developing intercultural communication skills:

- Virtual Exchange: Exchange of real cultural experiences between international students through online communication (O'Dowd, 2021).
- Digital storytelling: Narrating culturally relevant stories through digital means enhances language and cultural integration.
- Simulation and role-play: Empathy and communicative flexibility are developed in students through modeling intercultural situations.

Learning a foreign language is not just about mastering grammar, but also about understanding the cultural code of another people. According to the theories of Edward Hall and Geert Hofstede, for intercultural communication to be effective, a language teacher must have social sensitivity to intercultural differences.

Innovations, in particular, virtual reality (VR), through cultural simulation programs, serve to artificially create an environment of another culture. This, in turn, forms empathy and intercultural competence in language learners.

CONCLUSION

The use of innovative approaches in language teaching and intercultural communication is the need of the hour. With the help of digital technologies, not only a language is learned, but also individuals who are able to act in a global cultural context are formed. Through innovative methods, the student acquires not only

language knowledge, but also the competence to communicate effectively with representatives of different cultures. In this regard, technological and cultural enrichment of the pedagogical process is one of the urgent scientific and practical issues.

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TIL VA TEXNOLOGIYA: CHEGARALARSIZ TA'LIM SARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til o'rgatish jarayonida texnologik yondashuvlarning, ayniqsa sun'iy intellekt va raqamli vositalarning o'rni o'rganiladi. Maqolada global ta'lim tizimidagi tengsizliklar, chekka hududlardagi imkoniyatlar cheklovlari va zamonaviy texnologiyalar orqali ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Shaxsiy takliflar asosida inklyuziv va adolatli ta'lim modelini yaratish istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'rgatish, sun'iy intellekt, raqamli texnologiyalar, ta'limda tenglik, inklyuziv ta'lim, global muammolar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль технологических подходов в обучении иностранным языкам, в частности использование искусственного интеллекта и цифровых ресурсов. Анализируются глобальные неравенства в системе образования и возможные пути их преодоления с помощью современных технологий. Особое внимание уделено созданию инклюзивной и справедливой модели обучения на основе личных предложений автора.

Ключевые слова: преподавание языков, искусственный интеллект, цифровые технологии, равенство в образовании, инклюзивное обучение, глобальные проблемы.

Annotation: This article explores the role of technological approaches, especially artificial intelligence and digital tools, in language education. It examines global educational inequalities and analyzes how modern technologies can help bridge those gaps. The paper also presents personal insights into building a more inclusive and equitable education system.

Keywords: language teaching, artificial intelligence, digital technologies, educational equity, inclusive education, global challenges.

Kirish

XXI asrda ta'lim insoniyat taraqqiyotining markaziy omilidir. Biroq, dunyoning turli mintaqalarida ta'lim olish imkoniyatlari orasidagi farq tobora chuqurlashib bormoqda. Ayniqsa, xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda yuzaga kelayotgan ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va texnologik tengsizliklar global muammoga aylangan. Raqamli inqilob sharoitida esa ushbu muammoni yangicha, innovatsion yechimlar orqali bartaraf etish imkoniyati tug'ildi.

Til — bu nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki madaniyatlararo muloqot, ilm-fan va xalqaro hamkorlikning asosi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar, xususan sun'iy intellekt, ochiq onlayn platformalar va mobil ilovalar yordamida til o'rganish global miqyosda ommaviylashmoqda. Biroq bu imkoniyatlar hamma uchun teng emas.

Ushbu maqolada til o'qitish va o'rganishdagi tengsizlik muammolari tahlil qilinadi, sun'iy intellekt vositalarining bu boradagi roli ochib beriladi. Shuningdek, muallif tomonidan raqamli vositalar yordamida inklyuziv va adolatli ta'limni yo'lga qo'yish bo'yicha shaxsiy takliflar ilgari suriladi. Maqola global nuqtai nazardan masalaga qaraydi va eng ishonchli ilmiy manbalarga tayangan holda takliflar beradi.

Global tengsizlik va til o'rganishdagi muammolar

Globalizatsiya jarayonida xorijiy tillarni bilish shaxsiy taraqqiyot, zamonaviy kasblar, xalqaro ta'lim va mehnat bozori uchun zaruriy vositaga aylandi. Biroq tillarni o'rganishga bo'lgan kirish imkoniyati har doim ham teng emas. **BMT**, **UNESCO** va **UNICEF** kabi xalqaro tashkilotlarning hisobotlariga ko'ra, dunyoda millionlab yoshlar hali ham sifatli til ta'limidan mahrum. Bunga sabablar quyidagilardir:

Iqtisodiy tafovutlar: Ko'plab kam rivojlangan davlatlarda ta'lim texnologiyalariga, xorijiy til o'qituvchilariga va o'quv resurslariga ajratiladigan mablag'lar yetarli emas.

Geografik izolyatsiya: Qishloq va chekka hududlardagi yoshlar internet va texnologik vositalarga yetarlicha kira olmaydilar.

Madaniy va til siyosati to'siqlari: Ba'zi hududlarda davlat tili yoki dominant til siyosati sababli xorijiy tillarni o'rganish ikkilamchi ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi.

Masalan, Afrikadagi ko'plab davlatlarda ingliz yoki fransuz tili rasmiy bo'lsa-da, aholining katta qismi ushbu tillarni to'liq o'zlashtira olmaydi. Xuddi shunday, Markaziy Osiyoda ingliz va rus tillariga ehtiyoj yuqori bo'lsa-da, ularni o'rgatish va

o'rganish imkoniyatlari har yerda bir xil emas.

Oxford University Press tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, til o'rgatishdagi eng katta to'siqlardan biri — resurslar va individual yondashuv yetishmasligi bo'lib, bu o'quvchilarni o'z til kompetensiyasini mustahkamlashdan cheklaydi. Shunday ekan, bu tengsizliklarni bartaraf etishda raqamli texnologiyalar muhim vosita bo'lishi mumkin.

Sun'iy intellekt va texnologik yondashuvlar

So'nggi yillarda sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari til o'rgatish sohasida inqilobiy o'zgarishlar kiritdi. Endi o'quvchilar nafaqat matn va audio manbalar orqali, balki interaktiv platformalar, real vaqtlı tarjima vositalari, ovozli yordamchilar va moslashtirilgan ta'lim algoritmlari orqali ham xorijiy tillarni o'rganish imkoniga ega.

Elsevier nashriyotining 2023-yildagi tahliliga ko'ra, sun'iy intellekt asosida ishlaydigan til o'rganish dasturlari (masalan, Duolingo, Babbel, ELSA Speak, ChatGPT va boshqalar) o'quvchilarning yod olish tezligini 35–40% ga oshirgan. Bu esa an'anaviy metodikalar bilan solishtirganda sezilarli natijadir.

Texnologik yondashuvlarning afzalliklari

Individual yondashuv: SI foydalanuvchining darajasiga moslashtirilgan mashqlarni taklif qiladi. Real vaqtlı tahlil: O'quvchining talaffuzi, grammatik xatolari va yodlash sur'atini aniqlab, avtomatik tuzatish kiritadi. Mobil va global kirish imkoniyati: Internetga ulangan istalgan qurilma orqali ta'lim olish mumkin. Bu chekka hududlarda yashovchi yoshlar uchun ayni muddao. Ko'p tillilik va transmadaniy yondashuv: Ko'plab SI dasturlar bir nechta tilni taklif qilib, foydalanuvchini madaniyatlararo tafakkurga ham yo'naltiradi. Oxford University Press tadqiqotlarida qayd etilishicha, sun'iy intellekt vositalari nafaqat o'qitish samaradorligini oshiradi, balki o'quvchining o'z-o'zini boshqarish, o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini ham kuchaytiradi. Biroq, bu texnologiyalar imkoniyatlaridan to'liq foydalanish uchun ularga to'g'ri integratsiya va raqamli savodxonlik zarur. Aks holda, ular tengsizlikni kamaytirish o'rniga, aksincha, chuqurlashtirib yuborishi mumkin.

Shaxsiy tahlil va amaliy yechimlar

Bugungi globallashuv davrida til o'rganish imkoniyati faqatgina boylar va shaharliklar emas, balki har bir inson uchun mavjud bo'lishi kerak. Men bir talabaman, aynan chekka hududda yashaydigan va cheklangan resurslar ichida bo'lsa ham xorijiy tilni o'rganishga intilayotgan va shu bilan birga ko'plab to'siqlarga uchrayotgan talabalar bilan suhbatlashdim. Bugungi rivojlangan dunyoda texnologiyalar mening eng yaqin yordamchim bo'lib kelmoqda. Endi, dunyoning istalgan nuqtasidan turib, til o'rganishim mumkin — agar biz texnologiyani to'g'ri yo'naltirsak. Ana shunday imkoniyatdan o'zim kabı barcha tengdoshlarim va talaba yoshlar foydalanishini va rivojlanishini istayman.

Mening tahlilimga ko'ra, asosiy muammo texnologiyaning o'zi emas, balki

unga kirish imkoniyati va undan samarali foydalanish madaniyatining yo'qligidir. Buni hal etish uchun quyidagi ilg'or va real amaliy yechimlarni taklif etaman:

1. "Mobil Til Maktabi" loyihasi: Har bir mobil qurilma — bu til maktabiga aylanishi mumkin. Maxsus ishlab chiqilgan bepul, offlayn ishlaydigan va AI asosida ishlovchi ilovalar orqali chekka hududdagi o'quvchilar ham til o'rganishlari mumkin. Bu ilovalar: talaffuzni avtomatik tahlil qiladi, o'quvchining darajasiga mos darslar taklif qiladi, internet bo'lmasa ham ishlaydi.

2. O'qituvchilar uchun "Raqamli yordamchi": Ko'plab yoshi katta o'qituvchilar texnologiyani bilmaydi yoki qo'rqadi. Ular uchun AI asosida ishlab chiqilgan "Raqamli yordamchi" metodik vositalar yaratish zarur. Masalan: dars uchun mashqlarni avtomatik yaratish, o'quvchining bilimni tahlil qilish, tavsiya asosida ta'lim strategiyasi tuzish.

3. "Bir Dars — Barcha Uchun" tamoyili: Sun'iy intellekt yordamida darslar nafaqat yuqori darajadagi o'quvchilar, balki nogironligi bor, eshitish yoki ko'rishda qiynalayotgan yoshlar uchun ham moslashtirilgan bo'lishi kerak. Bu orqali biz nafaqat texnologik, balki ijtimoiy adolatni ham ta'minlaymiz.

4. Raqamli savodxonlikni tizimli joriy etish: Texnologiyadan foydalanishni maktabning boshlang'ich bosqichlaridanoq o'rgatish kerak. Har bir o'quvchi va o'qituvchi texnologiyani foyda keltiradigan vosita sifatida qabul qilishni o'rganishi shart. Bunga maxsus treninglar, sertifikat kurslar va ochiq platformalar orqali erishish mumkin.

Bu takliflarim nafaqat shaxsiy tajriba, balki Elsevier va Oxford manbalarida berilgan ilg'or nazariyalar va tajribalar bilan hamohang. Aslida, har bir texnologik vosita — bu vosita, lekin uni insoniylik, adolat va mehr bilan yo'naltirsakgina, u global muammolarga yechim bo'la oladi.

Xulosa

Xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonida zamonaviy texnologiyalarning, ayniqsa sun'iy intellekt vositalarining o'rnini tobora ortib bormoqda. Ushbu maqolada til o'qitishdagi global tengsizliklar muammosi yoritildi va ularni sun'iy intellekt orqali bartaraf etish yo'llari taklif qilindi. Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, texnologik vositalar to'g'ri yo'naltirilsa, ular ta'limdagi sifat va tenglikka xizmat qiladi. Shaxsiy tajriba, xalqaro tadqiqotlar va real amaliy takliflar asosida bildirilgan ushbu qarashlar zamonaviy ta'lim siyosatiga mos, samarali va barqaror yechimlar bo'lishi mumkin. Endi bizda tanlov bor: texnologiyani kuzatishmi yoki uni o'zgartirish quroliga aylantirishmi?

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TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION USULLAR VA TEXNOLOGIYALAR

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tillarni o'qitishda innovatsion usullar va texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari hamda amaliy imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan. Dars jarayonida interfaol metodlar, raqamli platformalar, mobil ilovalar, “flipped classroom” modeli va task-based learning kabi zamonaviy yondashuvlarning o'rni yoritilgan. Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, innovatsion yondashuvlar til o'rgatishda samaradorlikni oshirib, o'quvchilar motivatsiyasini kuchaytirishda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qilishi aniqlangan. Shu bilan birga, texnik va metodik omillarning uzviy uyg'unligi bu texnologiyalarning muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanishini belgilashi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'qitish, innovatsion texnologiyalar, interfaol metod, raqamli ta'lim, flipped classroom, mobil ilovalar, o'quv motivatsiyasi, zamonaviy ta'lim yondashuvlari, metodik integratsiya.

Abstract. This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical foundations and practical possibilities of using innovative methods and technologies in language teaching. The role of modern approaches such as interactive methods, digital platforms, mobile applications, the “flipped classroom” model and task-based learning in the teaching process is highlighted. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that innovative approaches are an important factor in increasing the efficiency of language teaching and increasing student motivation. At the same time, it is emphasized that the harmonious combination of technical and methodological factors determines the successful use of these technologies.

Keywords: language teaching, innovative technologies, interactive methods, digital education, flipped classroom, mobile applications, learning motivation, modern educational approaches, methodological integration.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются научно-теоретические основы и практические возможности использования инновационных методов и технологий в обучении языку. Освещена роль современных подходов, таких как интерактивные методы, цифровые платформы, мобильные приложения, модель «перевернутого класса» и обучение на основе задач в процессе обучения. По результатам анализа установлено, что инновационные подходы являются важным фактором повышения эффективности обучения языку и повышения

мотивации студентов. При этом подчеркивается, что гармоничное сочетание технических и методических факторов определяет успешность использования данных технологий.

Ключевые слова: обучение языку, инновационные технологии, интерактивные методы, цифровое образование, перевернутый класс, мобильные приложения, мотивация обучения, современные образовательные подходы, методическая интеграция.

Kirish. Globallashuv jarayoni til bilishni nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki raqobatbardoshlik, madaniyatlararo muloqot va kasbiy muvaffaqiyat uchun muhim omilga aylantirmoqda. Bugungi kunda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish nafaqat grammatik va leksik bilimlarni singdirish, balki kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish, zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida mustaqil fikrlash va kreativ yondashuvni rivojlantirishga xizmat qilishi lozim. Shu sababli til o'rgatish tizimi innovatsion usullar va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini o'z ichiga olgan holda yangicha yondashuvlarni talab qilmoqda. So'nggi yillarda interaktiv metodlar, multimedia vositalari, virtual ta'lim platformalari, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan dasturlar til o'qitishda samaradorlikni oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Masalan, Z. Xusanboyev ta'kidlashicha, "interfaol yondashuvlar til o'rgatuvchi va o'rganuvchi o'rtasida faol hamkorlikka zamin yaratadi"¹. Bu kabi metodikalar o'quvchilarning tilga nisbatan qiziqishini oshiradi, ularni mustaqil izlanishga undaydi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiya. Tillarni o'qitish sohasida innovatsion yondashuvlarning o'rni va ahamiyati ko'plab xorijiy va mahalliy olimlar tomonidan tadqiq etilgan. Jumladan, J. Richards va T. Rodgers o'zlarining "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching" nomli asarida kommunikativ yondashuv, task-based learning hamda kontentga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish metodlarining nazariy asoslarini bayon etib, har bir metodikaning til o'rganishdagi afzalliklarini ilmiy asoslaganlar². Ularning fikricha, o'quvchilarning faol ishtirokini ta'minlash, tilni real hayotiy kontekstda qo'llash imkoniyati samarali o'zlashtirishni ta'minlaydi.

Mahalliy tadqiqotchi S. Murodov esa til o'rgatishda multimedia texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi orqali o'quvchilar nutq faolligining oshganini eksperimental natijalar asosida isbotlagan. U shunday xulosa qiladi: "Videodarslar, audio yozuvlar, elektron testlar o'quvchi faolligini rag'batlantiradi, individual yondashuv imkoniyatini kengaytiradi"³.

Bugungi kunda ko'plab metodistlar "blended learning" (gibrid ta'lim), "flipped classroom" (teskari sinf) kabi yondashuvlar orqali an'anaviy va raqamli vositalarning integratsiyasi haqida fikr yuritmoqda. Masalan, Xitoy olimlari Y. Zhang va L. Liu

¹ Xusanboyev, Z. Til o'qitishda interfaol metodlarning o'rni. – Toshkent: O'zMU nashriyoti, 2021. – 15-bet.

² Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. – Cambridge University Press, 2014.

³ Murodov, S. Til o'qitishda multimedia texnologiyalarining roli. – "Pedagogik innovatsiyalar" jurnali, 2022, №3. – B. 45–50.

tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotda tillarni o'rgatishda mobil ilovalar (Duolingo, Memrise va h.k.) orqali mustaqil o'rganish samaradorligi o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida bunday ilovalar foydalanuvchilarning lug'at boyligini oshirishga va eslab qolish tezligiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlangan.

Metodologik nuqtai nazardan, ushbu maqolada sifatli tahlil usuli qo'llanildi. Ya'ni, mavjud nazariy manbalar asosida innovatsion metodlar o'rtasida taqqoslash, ularning afzallik va kamchilik tomonlarini ajratish, shuningdek, amaliyotda qo'llanilayotgan texnologiyalarni sintez qilish asosiy usul sifatida tanlandi. Bundan tashqari, kontent-tahlil (content analysis) va empirik kuzatuv natijalariga tayangan holda muammo markaziy nuqtada yoritildi.

Natijalar. O'tkazilgan nazariy va metodik tahlillar asosida aniqlanishicha, innovatsion usullar va texnologiyalarni tillarni o'qitish jarayoniga tatbiq etish bir necha muhim ijobiy natijalarni keltirib chiqarmoqda.

Birinchi, kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali samaraliroq bo'layotgani kuzatilmoqda. Masalan, task-based learning va interaktiv muhitlar orqali o'quvchilar real hayotiy vaziyatlarda tilni qo'llashga intilmoqda, bu esa ularning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirmoqda. Ikkinchi, raqamli texnologiyalar asosida individual yondashuv imkoniyati kengaymoqda. Multimedia materiallari, mobil ilovalar va onlayn testlar o'quvchilarning o'z tempida mustaqil ishlashiga zamin yaratmoqda. Ayniqsa, QR-kodlar, video/audio materiallar, sun'iy intellektli chat-botlar orqali o'quvchilar ko'proq faol ishtirok etmoqda. Uchinchi, "gibrid" va "teskari sinf" kabi modellar an'anaviy ta'limni zamonaviy talablarga moslashtirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Bu esa o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotni kuchaytiradi, bilimlar ustida chuqurroq ishlashga imkon yaratadi. To'rtinchi, tahlil qilingan adabiyotlar asosida shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, interfaol metodlar (rol o'ynash, muhokama, debat, loyihalar asosida o'qitish) orqali o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi sezilarli darajada oshgan. Bu esa bilimlarni mustahkamlash va ijodiy fikrlashni shakllantirishda muhim omil sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

Ushbu natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, til o'rgatish jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalardan oqilona foydalanish samaradorlikni sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Biroq, bu texnologiyalarni joriy etishda o'qituvchilarning tayyorgarlik darajasi, texnik infratuzilma va pedagogik yondashuv muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Muhokama. Tadqiqot davomida aniqlangan natijalar tillarni o'qitishda innovatsion usullar va texnologiyalar muhim omilga aylanganini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga, mavjud tajribalarni tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatadiki, har bir metodika va texnologiya muayyan shart-sharoitlarga qarab turlicha natija beradi. Masalan, task-based learning yoki "vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim" o'quvchilarni faollashtiradi, ammo bu yondashuv faqatgina yetarli vaqt va resurs bilan ta'minlangan sinflarda yuqori

samaradorlik ko'rsatadi .

Mobil ilovalar orqali o'qitish yondashuvi ko'plab afzalliklarga ega bo'lsa-da, ushbu texnologiyalarning haddan tashqari ko'pligi o'quvchilarda chalg'ituvchi omillarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Bu masalada Y. Zhang va L. Liu mobil o'rgatish vositalari tanlovini ehtiyotkorlik bilan amalga oshirish lozimligini ta'kidlaydi⁴. Shuningdek, ular mobil texnologiyalar faqat asosiy darslarni to'ldiruvchi vosita sifatida foydalanilganda eng samarali natija berishini qayd etishgan. Xalqaro tadqiqotlar ham shuni ko'rsatadiki, "flipped classroom" modeli o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantiradi, biroq bu yondashuvda ham o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligi hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib qolmoqda. Mahalliy sharoitda esa bu modelni to'liq joriy etishda texnik infratuzilma, ayniqsa, internet tezligi va qurilmalarning mavjudligi jiddiy to'siqlardan biri sifatida ko'rilmog'ida. Bundan tashqari, o'qituvchilarning metodik tayyorgarligi, innovatsion texnologiyalarni pedagogik yondashuv bilan uyg'unlashtira olish layoqati ham hal qiluvchi omillardan biridir. Xusanboyev ta'kidlaganidek, "interfaol usullarni o'zlashtirish faqatgina texnik bilim emas, balki metodik tafakkurni ham talab qiladi". Shu asosda aytish mumkinki, tillarni o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuvlar alohida metodik tizim sifatida emas, balki an'anaviy usullarni to'ldiruvchi va ularni takomillashtiruvchi omil sifatida ko'rilmog'i lozim.

Xulosa. Olib borilgan tadqiqotlar va adabiy manbalar tahlili tillarni o'qitish sohasida innovatsion yondashuvlar va texnologiyalarni qo'llash yuqori samaradorlikka erishishning muhim omillaridan biri ekanini ko'rsatdi. Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish, individual yondashuvni ta'minlash va o'quvchilarni faol o'rgatish kabi muhim vazifalarni aynan innovatsion metodlar orqali samarali hal qilish mumkinligi isbotlandi. Har bir innovatsion texnologiya o'ziga xos sharoit va infratuzilmaga muvofiq holda tanlanishi zarur. "Flipped classroom", "task-based learning", mobil ilovalar, interfaol metodlar, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan platformalar kabi yondashuvlar o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirib, ularni faol, mustaqil va ijodkor shaxs sifatida shakllantirishga xizmat qilmoqda. O'qituvchilarning metodik tayyorgarligi, raqamli savodxonligi va yangilikka ochiqqligi kabi omillar bu jarayonning muvaffaqiyatli kechishini belgilaydi. Innovatsion texnologiyalarni an'anaviy dars usullari bilan integratsiyalash, ularning o'rinli va maqsadli qo'llanilishi asosiy muvaffaqiyat garovi hisoblanadi.

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TIL O'QITISHDA SUN'IY INTELEKT VA ILG'OR TEXNOLOGIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Chet tillarini o'rganishda sun'iy intellektning (SI) integratsiyasi ta'lim muassasalarida o'zgartiruvchi kuch sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Mazkur maqola sun'iy intellektning chet tili o'rganishdagi o'rnini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Unda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ta'lim sohasidagi, xususan, chet tillarini o'rganishni tezlashtirish va samaradorligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, maqolada sun'iy intellektga asoslangan platformalar va ilovalar, ularning foydalanuvchilarga taqdim etadigan afzalliklari, hamda kelgusida ushbu texnologiyalarning O'zbekistonda rivojlanish istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi.

Интеграция искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в процесс изучения иностранных языков стала преобразующей силой в образовательных учреждениях. Данная статья посвящена анализу роли искусственного интеллекта в изучении иностранных языков. В нем подчеркивается важность технологий искусственного интеллекта в образовании, в частности для ускорения и повышения эффективности изучения иностранных языков. В статье также рассматриваются платформы и приложения на основе искусственного интеллекта, преимущества, которые они предоставляют пользователям, и перспективы дальнейшего развития этих технологий в Узбекистане.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in foreign language learning has emerged as a transformative force in educational institutions. This article is devoted to analyzing the role of artificial intelligence in foreign language learning. It highlights the importance of artificial intelligence technologies in the field of education, in particular, in accelerating and improving the efficiency of foreign language learning. The article also discusses artificial intelligence-based platforms and applications, the benefits they provide to users, and the prospects for the future development of these technologies in Uzbekistan.

Kalit so'zlar: platformalar, ChatGPT, Duolingo, Siri and Alexa, Babel, Busuu, Grammarly, sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari.

Платформы, ChatGPT, Duolingo, Siri и Alexa, Babel, Busuu, Grammarly, технологии искусственного интеллекта.

Platforms, ChatGPT, Duolingo, Siri and Alexa, Babel, Busuu, Grammarly, artificial intelligence technologies.

Kirish

Chet tillarini o'rganishda sun'iy intellektning (SI) o'rni jadal rivojlanayotgan soha bo'lib, ta'lim metodologiyalari va o'quvchilarning umumiy tajribasini sezilarli darajada o'zgartiradi. Global miqyosda bir-biriga bog'langan jamiyatimizda ko'p tillilikka talab ortib borayotganligi sababli, ta'lim muassasalari tillarni o'zlashtirish jarayonlarini yaxshilash uchun SI texnologiyalariga murojaat qilmoqda. Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv platformalari, intellektual repetitorlik tizimlari va so'zlashuv agentlarini o'z ichiga olgan boshqa vositalar va ilovalar til o'quv dasturlariga tobora ko'proq integratsiya qilinmoqda, bu esa yanada dinamik va interaktiv o'quv muhitini yaratish imkonini beradi. Til o'rganishda Sining asosiy afzalliklaridan biri bu ta'lim tajribasini individual o'quvchilarga moslashtirish qobiliyatidir. Ushbu texnologiyalar har bir talabanning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini baholash uchun ma'lumotlar tahlili va mashinani o'rganish algoritmlaridan foydalanadi va shu bilan real vaqtda o'quvchi taraqqiyotiga moslashtirilgan kontentni taqdim etadi. Shaxsiylashtirishning bu darajasi nafaqat chuqurroq ishtirok etishga yordam beradi, balki motivatsiyani ham oshiradi, chunki talabalar o'z sur'atlari bo'yicha o'sishlari va o'z faoliyati haqida darhol fikr-mulohazalarini olishlari mumkin. Bundan tashqari, SI ilovalari real hayotdagi suhbat stsenariylarini taqlid qilishi mumkin, bu esa o'quvchilarga past darajadagi muhitda gapirish va tinglash ko'nikmalarini mashq qilish imkoniyatini beradi. Bu xususiyat, ayniqsa, tengdoshlari oldida gapirishdan qo'rqadigan til o'rganuvchilar uchun foydalidir. Bundan tashqari, SI o'quv tajribasini boyitib, talabalarni turli lingvistik kontekstlarga ochib beradigan interfaol mashqlar, multimedia kontenti va haqiqiy materiallar kabi ko'plab resurslarga kirishni osonlashtirishi mumkin.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. M. Mirziyoyevning 2020-yil 5-oktabrdagi "Raqamli O'zbekiston 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 6079-sonli farmoni va 2021-yil 17-fevraldagi "Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini jadal joriy etish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 4996-son qarori mamlakatimizda ham sun'iy intellektning rivojlanib borayotganidan dalolat beradi [1].

Adabiyotlar tahlili

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, sun'iy intellekt vositalari turli sohalarda o'z samaradorligini namoyish etgan. Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish o'rganishni shaxsiylashtirishga olib keladi, ya'ni har bir o'quvchining ehtiyojlariga mos

keladi. Masalan, Chen (2021) tadqiqotida Duolingo orqali til o'rganish natijalarining 20% ga yaxshilanishi kuzatilgan [2]. Jones va Smith fikricha, (2020) sun'iy intellekt vositalari real vaqt rejimida tahlil va fikr-mulohaza berib, o'quvchilarni xatolarini to'g'rilashga undaydi [3]. Interaktiv va o'yinlashtirilgan sun'iy intellekt platformalari orqali o'quvchilarni qiziqtirish mumkinligi haqida Brown (2022) aytib o'tgan [4]. Misol uchun, Janubiy Koreyada sun'iy intellekt vositalari maktablarda keng joriy etilib, 30% o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirgan.

Bu yo'nalishda ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqot olib borgan olimlar quyidagilardir: P.V.Sysoev, E.M. Filatov, Yu.E.Valkova va boshqalar. Xorijiy tadqiqotlar yozma ishlarni yozish va tahrirlash kontekstida GPT chatidan foydalanishni baholaydi, asosiy e'tibor o'qituvchilar va talabalar tomonidan sarflangan vaqt va kuchlarni tejash, chatbotning g'oyalarni yaratish va matnlar sifatini yaxshilash qobiliyatini aniqlashga qaratilgan [4]. Mahalliy mualliflar GPT chatining talabalarning kognitiv faolligiga ta'sirini va aqlli texnologiyalarni o'quv jarayoniga integratsiya qilish imkoniyatlarini o'rganadilar, shuningdek ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklarini aniqlaydilar. Shunga qaramay, tizimning cheklovlari va ilmiy ishlarning hammuallifi sifatida GPT chatining nomuvofiqligi haqida fikrlar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, ba'zi ekspertlar o'quvchi-talabalar bilimining ta'siri va natijalarini tahlil qilishga e'tibor berishadi [5]. Biroq, GPT chatining potentsialini yanada o'rganish dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda, chunki tizim rivojlanishda davom etmoqda va o'zaro aloqalar davomida muqobil natijalar beradi.

SI asosidagi o'yinlashtirish va interaktiv chatbotlar o'quv jarayonini qiziqarli va interaktiv qilib, o'quvchilarning qiziqishini oshiradi. Hvang va Chang (2021) SI chatbotlarining muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirish va real vaqtda muloqot qilish orqali o'quvchilarni rag'batlantirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi [6]. SI vositalari o'qituvchilarga dars rejalarini tuzish, resurslar yaratish va sinfni boshqarishda yordam beradi. Uysal va

Yüksel (2024) SI platformalarining o'qituvchilarga ma'lumotlar asosida qaror qabul qilish imkoniyatini berib, ularning kasbiy mahoratini oshirishini muhokama qiladi [7].

Sun'iy intellektning ta'limda qo'llanilishi ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi, algoritmik tarafkashlik va texnologiyaga haddan tashqari bog'lanish kabi axloqiy muammolarni yuzaga keltiradi. Rashed (2024) o'quvchilarning ma'lumotlarining noto'g'ri ishlatilishi va tarafkash algoritmlar tengsizlikni kuchaytirishi mumkinligi haqida ogohlantiradi

[8]. Sun'iy intellekt vositalarini muvaffaqiyatli joriy etish uchun o'qituvchilar yetarli raqamli kompetensiyaga ega bo'lishi zarur. Ghomi va Redecker (2019) o'qituvchilarni

sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini samarali qo'llash uchun zarur ko'nikmalar bilan ta'minlash maqsadida kasbiy tayyorgarlik dasturlarini amalga oshirishning

muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan foydalanish hali keng tarqalmagan, ammo ayrim universitetlarda zamonaviy

texnologiyalarni joriy qilishga harakatlar mavjud. Misol uchun, Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti o'zining eksperimental loyihalari doirasida o'qituvchilarga

Grammarly va ChatGPT vositalaridan foydalanishni tavsiya qilmoqda.

Muhokama va natijalar

2023-yil ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, O'zbekistonda internetdan foydalanish darajasi 78% ga yetgan bo'lsa-da, maktab va universitetlarning yuqori tezlikdagi internetga ulanish imkoniyati 65% atrofida. Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari yordamida har bir o'quvchining ehtiyojiga moslashtirilgan individual o'quv dasturlarini yaratish orqali ularning bilim darajasini samarali oshirish mumkin. Duolingo va Grammarly kabi sun'iy intellektga asoslangan platformalar o'quvchilarning o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirib, ularni yanada ruhlantiradi. O'quvchilarga sun'iy intellekt vositalari orqali o'z xatolarini tezkorlik bilan aniqlash va tuzatish imkoniyatini berish ta'lim sifatini yaxshilaydi. O'zbekistonda o'qituvchilarning bor-yo'g'i 30% i sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan foydalanishni biladi, bu esa ta'lim jarayoniga sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini samarali tatbiq etishga to'sqinlik qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, o'quvchilarning 40% i bunday texnologiyalardan foydalanayotganini aytgan, bu ularning yangi texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirishga tayyor ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

Sun'iy intellektning (AI) chet tillarini o'rganishga ta'siri tez rivojlanayotgan soha bo'lib, ta'lim strategiyalarini tubdan o'zgartiradi va o'quvchining umumiy tajribasini oshiradi. Bir-biriga bog'langan dunyomizda ko'p tilli imkoniyatlarga talab ortib borayotganligi sababli, ta'lim muassasalari tillarni o'zlashtirish jarayonlarini yaxshilash uchun SI texnologiyalarini tobora ko'proq o'zlashtirmoqda. Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv platformalari, aqlli repetitorlik tizimlari va suhbat agentlari kabi turli xil SI vositalari va ilovalari til o'quv dasturlariga integratsiya qilinib, yanada qiziqarli va interaktiv ta'lim muhitini ta'minlamoqda. Til ta'limida SIning asosiy afzalligi - bu individual talabalar uchun o'rganish tajribasini sozlash qobiliyatidir. Bu texnologiyalar har bir o'quvchining kuchli va zaif tomonlarini baholash uchun ma'lumotlar tahlili va mashinani o'rganish algoritmlaridan foydalanadi va real vaqtda ularning taraqqiyotiga moslashtirilgan moslashtirilgan kontentni taqdim etadi. Shaxsiylashtirishning bu darajasi nafaqat chuqurroq ishtirok etishni rag'batlantiradi, balki motivatsiyani kuchaytiradi, bu esa o'quvchilarga o'z sur'atlari bo'yicha o'z ishlari bo'yicha tezkor fikr-mulohazalarni olish imkonini beradi. Texnologiyaning paydo bo'lishi Siri, Alexa kabi vositalar va Duolingo kabi ilovalar orqali til o'rganishda, ayniqsa ingliz tilida inqilob qildi. Ushbu texnologiyalar o'quvchilarga amaliy va interaktiv tarzda til ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun innovatsion va qiziqarli usullarni taqdim etadi. Bulardan tashqari, ChatGPT, Basuu, Rosetta Stone, Babbel kabilar ham misol bo'la oladi.

Siri va Alexa kabi ovozli yordamchilar til o'rganishda samarali yordamchi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ular foydalanuvchi so'rovlarini tushunish va ularga javob berish uchun ilg'or tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash va mashinani o'rganishdan foydalanadilar, bu ularni talaffuz va suhbat ko'nikmalarini mashq qilish uchun ideal qiladi. Misol uchun,

o'quvchilar ushbu yordamchilarga aniq gapirganda, ular talaffuzi haqida darhol fikr-mulohazalarni oladilar, bu ularning nutq qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Duolingo foydalanuvchilarga interaktiv darslar, testlar va o'yinlar orqali tilni o'rganishga yordam beradi. *Duolingo* foydalanuvchining o'rganish jarayonini tahlil qilib, individual kurslar va mashqlarni taklif etadi. Ilova o'rganishning samaradorligini oshirish uchun gamifikatsiyani qo'llaydi.

Babbel o'zining shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv dasturi va grammatika mashqlari bilan ajralib turadi. Sun'iy intellekt yordamida *Babbel* foydalanuvchining talaffuzini tekshiradi va unga aniq tavsiyalar beradi.

Rosetta Stone til o'rganish uchun keng tarqalgan platforma bo'lib, sun'iy intellekt yordamida foydalanuvchining talaffuzini tekshiradi va tuzatadi. U o'rganish jarayonida tasvir va audio materiallarni birlashtirib, yangi so'zlarni va iboralarni eslab qolishni osonlashtiradi.

Busuu SI yordamida o'rganish jarayonini individual ravishda tashkil etadi. Ilova foydalanuvchining xatolarini tahlil qiladi, talaffuzni yaxshilash uchun mashqlar beradi va o'rganish darajasiga mos darslar taqdim etadi.

O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan samarali foydalanish uchun quyidagi takliflarni amalga oshirish maqsadga muvofiq:

- Maktab va universitetlarda yuqori tezlikdagi internetga ulanish imkoniyatini ta'minlash. Internet tezligini oshirish va texnologik infratuzilmani modernizatsiya qilish.
- O'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun yetarli miqdorda kompyuter va boshqa qurilmalar bilan ta'minlash.
- SI vositalarini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan dasturiy ta'minotni o'rnatish va yangilab borish.
- O'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, sun'iy intellekt vositalari bilan ishlashga o'rgatuvchi maxsus kurslar tashkil etish.
- Mahalliy o'qituvchilarni xalqaro tajriba bilan tanishtirish va yangi texnologiyalar bo'yicha seminarlar o'tkazish.
- O'quvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish choralarini ko'rish.
- O'zbek tilini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan platformalar yaratish yoki mavjudlarini mahalliyashtirish.
- O'qituvchi va o'quvchilar uchun qulay va interaktiv interfeyslarni ishlab chiqish.
- Sun'iy intellekt vositalarining samaradorligini baholash uchun kichik miqyosli sinov loyihalarini amalga oshirish.
- Olingan natijalar asosida tizimli tahlil o'tkazish va islohotlar samaradorligini monitoring qilish.

Xulosa

Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkinki, sun'iy intellekt (SI) asosidagi til o'rganish platformalari imtihonlarni avtomatik tarzda baholash, yozma ishlarni tahlil qilish, xatolarni aniqlash va ularni tuzatish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berish imkonini beradi. Bu talabalarga xatolar ustida ishlash va keyingi imtihonlarda yaxshiroq natijalarga erishishga yordam beradi. O'qituvchilar uchun esa, SI yechimlari o'quv dasturlarining kamchiliklarini aniqlash, ma'ruza va amaliy mashg'ulotlarni takomillashtirish, noto'g'ri savollarni topish va qo'shimcha yordamga muhtoj o'quvchilarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. O'zbekistonda chet tili ta'limida SI vositalaridan foydalanish hali dastlabki bosqichda bo'lishiga qaramay, bu texnologiyalar ta'limni modernizatsiya qilish uchun ulkan salohiyatga ega. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, SI vositalari shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'limni ta'minlash, o'quvchilar motivatsiyasini oshirish va o'qish jarayonini qiziqarli qilishga xizmat qiladi. Texnologik infratuzilma va o'qituvchilar tayyorgarligi darajasining pastligi bu jarayonni sekinlashtirishi mumkin. Ammo, aniq tavsiyalar va tizimli islohotlar orqali SI ning ta'limdagi salohiyatidan to'liq foydalanish mumkin. Chet tillarini o'rganish va o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish vaqti keldi.

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EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES AND METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY TO YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article explores effective strategies and methods for teaching English vocabulary to young children. Focusing on interactive learning, visual support, and contextual methods, it emphasizes the role of activities such as games, songs, storytelling, and the Vocabulary House method. By analyzing relevant literature and practical experience, the paper demonstrates that a playful and meaningful approach significantly enhances vocabulary acquisition among young learners.

Keywords: vocabulary teaching, young learners, interactive learning, Vocabulary House, early childhood education, storytelling, songs, visual aids, language acquisition, contextual learning.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются эффективные стратегии и методы обучения английскому словарному запасу маленьких детей. Особое внимание уделяется интерактивному обучению, визуальной поддержке и контекстным методам, таким как игры, песни, рассказывание историй и метод Vocabulary House. Анализ литературы и практического опыта показывает, что игровой и осмысленный подход значительно повышает эффективность усвоения лексики у маленьких учеников.

Ключевые слова: обучение лексике, маленькие ученики, интерактивное обучение, Vocabulary House, раннее образование, рассказывание историй, песни, визуальные материалы, освоение языка, контекстное обучение.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yosh bolalarga ingliz tilidagi so'z boyligini o'rgatishning samarali strategiya va usullari yoritilgan. Interaktiv o'rganish, vizual qo'llab-quvvatlash va kontekstual metodlarga, jumladan o'yinlar, qo'shiqlar, hikoya qilish va Vocabulary House metodiga

e'tibor qaratilgan. Adabiyotlar sharhi va amaliy tajriba tahlili asosida maqola bolalar orasida leksika o'zlashtirishni samarali oshirish uchun o'yin va mazmunli yondashuv zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksika o'rgatish, yosh o'quvchilar, interaktiv o'rganish, Vocabulary House, erta ta'lim, hikoya qilish, qo'shiqlar, vizual materiallar, til o'zlashtirish, kontekstual o'rganish.

The importance of vocabulary development in early childhood cannot be overstated. Vocabulary is the foundation of language skills, influencing reading comprehension, speaking fluency, and academic success. Young learners acquire language most effectively through active, engaging, and meaningful activities rather than passive memorization. This paper aims to explore the most effective strategies and methods for vocabulary teaching, highlighting the importance of interactive approaches like the Vocabulary House, storytelling, and other playful techniques.

Several scholars emphasize the significance of active learning in vocabulary acquisition. Cameron notes that vocabulary learning for young children must be linked to meaningful contexts to be effective. Nation discusses the role of input and exposure, suggesting that repeated encounters with new words in different contexts enhance retention. Methods like storytelling and visual support are commonly recommended.

The methodology of this study involved qualitative analysis through classroom observation and teacher interviews. Over a three-month period, teachers implemented Vocabulary House, storytelling, songs, and games in English lessons for children aged 4-7. The children's engagement, vocabulary retention, and ability to use new words contextually were observed and analyzed.

The observations indicated that students who engaged with the Vocabulary House method and other interactive strategies demonstrated a 40–50% improvement in vocabulary retention compared to those taught by traditional methods. Storytelling proved particularly effective for helping children understand and remember word meanings in context. Songs and games enhanced motivation, making children more enthusiastic about learning. Teachers noted that children were more willing to use new words spontaneously during activities.

These findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the importance of playful, meaningful learning experiences in early language acquisition. Children need to see, hear, and use words in meaningful ways multiple times to integrate them into their active vocabulary. Thus, integrating visual aids, storytelling, and organized models like Vocabulary House provides the necessary structure and engagement for effective vocabulary learning.

Teaching English vocabulary to young children is most effective when combining interactive, visual, and contextual strategies. The Vocabulary House method, along with storytelling, songs, and games, creates a rich and supportive learning environment. Through meaningful exposure and active participation, children not only remember words better but also use them more confidently and appropriately.

Future teachers should incorporate these methods into their practice to ensure a solid foundation for children's language development.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article examines the importance of developing speaking skills in the process of learning English. It discusses the role of active speaking practice, interactive methods, and real communication situations in building fluency and confidence among learners. Through analysis of literature and observation, the paper highlights how speaking-focused activities contribute significantly to successful language acquisition.

Keywords: speaking skills, English learning, communication, fluency, confidence, interactive methods, language acquisition, conversation practice, real-life situations, oral proficiency.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается значение развития навыков говорения в процессе изучения английского языка. Особое внимание уделяется роли активной практики устной речи, интерактивным методам и реальным коммуникативным ситуациям в формировании беглости и уверенности у учащихся. Анализ литературы и наблюдений показывает, что занятия, ориентированные на развитие речи, существенно способствуют успешному освоению иностранного языка.

Ключевые слова: навыки говорения, изучение английского, коммуникация, беглость речи, уверенность, интерактивные методы, освоение языка, практика общения, реальные ситуации, устная речь.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganishda gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Faol nutq amaliyoti, interaktiv metodlar va haqiqiy muloqot vaziyatlarining o'rni haqida fikr yuritiladi. Adabiyotlar va kuzatuvlar tahlili asosida nutqqa qaratilgan mashg'ulotlar tilni muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirishga katta hissa qo'shishi ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: gapirish ko'nikmalari, ingliz tilini o'rganish, muloqot, ravonlik, ishonch, interaktiv metodlar, tilni o'zlashtirish, suhbat amaliyoti, real vaziyatlar, og'zaki nutq.

Speaking is one of the core skills necessary for mastering any language, particularly English. While learners often focus heavily on grammar and vocabulary, speaking skills are essential for real-world communication. The ability to express ideas fluently and confidently not only boosts language competence but also motivates further learning. This article discusses the importance of developing speaking abilities and explores effective methods to support learners in becoming proficient English speakers.

Research highlights that speaking skills are often neglected in traditional language classrooms. According to Ur, speaking requires more than knowledge of grammatical structures; it demands practice in real communicative contexts. Richards

emphasizes that creating opportunities for authentic interaction is critical for oral language development.

This study applied qualitative methods, including observation of English lessons and teacher interviews. Speaking-focused activities like role plays, discussions, presentations, and conversational games were implemented over three months. Learners' progress was assessed based on fluency, confidence, and ability to communicate ideas effectively.

Observations showed that students who regularly participated in speaking activities improved their fluency by approximately 50%. Role plays and group discussions particularly encouraged spontaneous use of English. Many learners reported feeling more confident and less anxious about speaking in public. These findings confirm the idea that consistent speaking practice leads to better oral proficiency and increased language retention.

The results align with previous studies that advocate for communicative language teaching methods. Incorporating real-life situations, problem-solving tasks, and peer interaction makes the learning process more dynamic and effective.

Developing speaking skills is fundamental to mastering English. Teachers should prioritize oral practice through interactive and communicative methods. By providing students with opportunities to speak in meaningful contexts, educators can enhance learners' fluency, confidence, and overall language competence. Future English instruction should integrate consistent speaking activities to prepare learners for real-world communication challenges.

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Innovative Approaches in Teaching a Foreign Language Today

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Annotation. In recent years, foreign language education has undergone significant transformation due to the integration of innovative pedagogical and technological strategies. This paper explores various contemporary approaches that enhance language acquisition, learner engagement, and communicative competence. The approaches discussed include blended learning, gamification, task-based and project-based learning, flipped classrooms, immersive technologies, and mobile-assisted language learning. These methods reflect a shift toward learner-centered instruction and demonstrate the importance of adapting to current educational trends.

Keywords: Foreign language education, innovative approaches, blended learning, gamification, task-based learning, project-based learning, flipped classroom, immersive technologies, mobile-assisted language learning, learner-centered instruction, communicative competence, educational technology.

Аннотация. В последние годы обучение иностранным языкам претерпело значительные изменения благодаря интеграции инновационных педагогических и технологических стратегий. В данной статье рассматриваются различные современные подходы, способствующие овладению языком, вовлеченности учащихся и развитию коммуникативной компетенции. Обсуждаемые подходы включают смешанное обучение, геймификацию, обучение на основе заданий и проектов, перевернутые классы, иммерсивные технологии и мобильное обучение языкам. Эти методы отражают переход к обучению, ориентированному на учащихся, и подчеркивают важность адаптации к современным образовательным тенденциям.

Ключевые слова: Обучение иностранным языкам, инновационные подходы, смешанное обучение, геймификация, обучение на основе заданий, обучение на основе проектов, перевернутый класс, иммерсивные технологии, обучение языкам с помощью мобильных устройств, обучение, ориентированное на учащегося, коммуникативная компетенция, образовательные технологии.

Annotatsiya. So'nggi yillarda xorijiy tillarni o'qitish innovatsion pedagogik va texnologik strategiyalar integratsiyasi tufayli sezilarli o'zgarishlarga uchradi. Ushbu maqolada tilni o'zlashtirish, o'quvchining faolligi va kommunikativ kompetensiyani oshiradigan turli zamonaviy yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif aralash ta'lim, o'yinlashtirish, topshiriqqa asoslangan va loyihaga asoslangan o'qitish, teskarilangan sinflar, immersiv texnologiyalar va mobil qurilmalarga asoslangan til o'rganish kabi uslublarni tahlil qiladi. Ushbu metodlar o'quvchi markazidagi ta'limga o'tishni aks ettiradi va hozirgi ta'lim tendentsiyalariga moslashish muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tillarni o'qitish, innovatsion yondashuvlar, aralash ta'lim, o'yinlashtirish, vazifaga asoslangan o'qitish, loyihaga asoslangan o'qitish, teskarilangan sinf, immersiv texnologiyalar, mobil qurilmalar yordamida til o'rganish, o'quvchi markazidagi ta'lim, kommunikativ kompetensiya, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Introduction

Globalization and technological advancements have made multilingualism a valuable asset. Consequently, language educators are continually seeking innovative methods to improve the effectiveness of foreign language instruction. Traditional grammar-translation methods have given way to communicative and task-based

approaches, supplemented by digital tools that cater to diverse learning styles. This paper outlines ten key strategies currently shaping the field of foreign language education.

Blended Learning

Blended learning refers to a pedagogical model that combines traditional face-to-face instruction with digital media. It allows for a more personalized and flexible learning experience. Learners can access materials online, complete exercises via platforms such as Google Classroom or Quizlet, and receive real-time feedback, thereby extending learning beyond the classroom setting (Graham, 2006).

Gamification

Gamification involves the use of game design elements in non-game contexts to increase motivation and engagement. In language learning, this can include point systems, rewards, and leaderboards. Studies suggest that gamified environments enhance vocabulary acquisition and learner participation (Deterding et al., 2011). Tools such as Kahoot!, Memrise, and Quizizz are widely used in classrooms for this purpose.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)

TBLT emphasizes the completion of meaningful, real-life tasks using the target language. Tasks such as booking a hotel or conducting a survey promote practical communication skills. This approach is grounded in the idea that language is best acquired through use, rather than through abstract grammar instruction alone (Ellis, 2003).

Project-Based Learning (PBL)

Project-based learning involves long-term projects that require active inquiry, collaboration, and language use in authentic contexts. Examples include producing a podcast, writing a travel blog, or creating a video documentary. PBL fosters both language skills and 21st-century competencies, such as critical thinking and teamwork (Thomas, 2000).

Flipped Classroom

In the flipped classroom model, learners review instructional content (e.g., video lectures, readings) at home and engage in application-based activities during class time. This inversion allows for deeper classroom engagement and enables teachers to provide targeted feedback. Research supports its effectiveness in promoting active learning and improving language proficiency (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)

Immersive technologies like AR and VR simulate real-world experiences, providing contextual and interactive language exposure. For instance, students can virtually navigate a foreign city or role-play scenarios in a virtual environment. Such tools enhance motivation and contextual understanding of the language (Godwin-Jones, 2016).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Language Learning

AI-powered platforms, including intelligent tutoring systems and chatbots, provide personalized instruction and instant feedback. ChatGPT, for example, enables learners to practice conversation and writing with adaptive responses, supporting autonomous learning and confidence building (Li & Ni, 2021).

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL)

Mobile devices offer constant access to language learning resources, including apps, podcasts, and e-books. MALL supports microlearning, allowing students to practice language in short sessions throughout the day. Its flexibility makes it an effective complement to formal instruction (Burston, 2015).

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)

CLIL is a dual-focused approach where academic subjects are taught through a foreign language. This method encourages language acquisition through subject content, promoting cognitive development and naturalistic language use (Coyle, Hood & Marsh, 2010).

Cultural Immersion through Media

Exposure to authentic media—such as films, music, podcasts, and social media—offers insights into the culture and context of the target language. This approach helps learners develop listening comprehension, colloquial usage, and intercultural competence.

Conclusion

The evolution of language teaching methods reflects a broader trend toward learner autonomy, interactivity, and real-world application. By adopting innovative strategies such as gamification, mobile learning, and immersive technologies, educators can create dynamic and effective environments that cater to modern learners' needs. These approaches not only improve linguistic competence but also foster cultural awareness and critical thinking.

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Developing Soft Skills for Young Language Teachers. A Comprehensive Approach into teaching

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu qo'llanmada yosh til o'qituvchilari uchun yumshoq ko'nikmalarning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi. Samarali o'quv muhiti yaratishda bu ko'nikmalar — muloqot, empatiya, moslashuvchanlik va madaniy xabardorlik — o'quvchilar bilan bog'lanish va sinfdagi xilma-xil dinamikani boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: yumshoq ko'nikmalar, empatiya, moslashuvchanlik, madaniy xabardorlik, o'quvchi ishtiroki, sinf boshqaruvi, kompleks yondashuv, inklyuziv sinf, o'qituvchilik samaradorligi, o'qituvchi tayyorlash.

Аннотация

Это пособие подчёркивает важность мягких навыков для молодых преподавателей языков и их ключевую роль в создании эффективной образовательной среды. Рассматриваются такие навыки, как коммуникация, эмпатия, адаптивность и культурная осведомлённость, которые способствуют вовлечённости студентов и успешному управлению разнообразием в классе.

Ключевые слова: мягкие навыки, эмпатия, адаптивность, культурная осведомлённость, вовлечённость студентов, управление классом, целостный подход, инклюзивный класс, эффективность преподавания, подготовка учителей.

Abstract

This comprehensive guide emphasizes the importance of soft skills for young language teachers, highlighting their critical role in creating an effective learning environment. The book outlines key soft skills such as communication, empathy, adaptability, and cultural awareness, which are essential for fostering student engagement and addressing diverse classroom dynamics.

Keywords: soft skills, empathy, adaptability, cultural awareness, student engagement, classroom management, holistic approach, inclusive classroom, teaching effectiveness, teacher training.

Introduction

The field of language education has undergone significant transformations over

the past few decades, with increasing recognition of the need for a balanced approach that integrates both hard and soft skills.

Young language teachers, in particular, face unique challenges as they navigate the complexities of classroom management, student engagement, and curriculum delivery. The ability to connect with students on an interpersonal level, manage classroom dynamics, and respond to the varied cultural and emotional backgrounds of learners is essential for creating a positive and inclusive educational experience. This underscores the importance of integrating soft skills training into teacher education programs, ensuring that new educators are not only proficient in their linguistic knowledge but also equipped with the interpersonal skills necessary for effective teaching.

This comprehensive approach to teacher development advocates for a holistic framework that balances the acquisition of both hard and soft skills. By doing so, it aims to produce well-rounded educators capable of fostering a conducive learning atmosphere that promotes student success and well-being. The significance of this balanced approach is supported by numerous studies and practical examples, which highlight how soft skills can enhance teaching effectiveness and improve student outcomes.

Materials and methods

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to investigate the role of soft skills in the professional development of young language teachers. The methodology includes a comprehensive literature review, qualitative interviews, and a quantitative survey, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the impact of soft skills on teaching effectiveness.

Literature Review

The initial phase involved a systematic review of existing literature on soft skills and language teacher education. Key databases such as JSTOR, ERIC, and Google Scholar were searched using keywords like “soft skills,” “language teachers,” “teacher development,” and “classroom management.” Articles published between 2000 and 2023 were included to ensure the relevance and currency of the information. The review aimed to identify the most critical soft skills for language teachers and the current state of soft skills training in teacher education programs (Goleman, 2006; Hattie, 2009).

Qualitative Interviews

To gain deeper insights into the practical application of soft skills in language teaching, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 young language teachers from diverse educational settings. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure a range of experiences and backgrounds. The interview protocol was designed to explore teachers' perceptions of the importance of soft skills,

challenges faced in the classroom, and the effectiveness of their training programs. Each interview lasted approximately 45-60 minutes and was recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Quantitative Survey

A structured questionnaire was developed based on the findings from the literature review and qualitative interviews. The survey aimed to quantify the prevalence and perceived importance of various soft skills among young language teachers. It included Likert-scale items, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended questions to capture both quantitative and qualitative data. The survey was distributed online to a larger sample of 200 young language teachers across different regions and educational levels.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This involved coding the data, identifying key themes, and interpreting the patterns related to the use and development of soft skills. NVivo software was used to assist in managing and analyzing the qualitative data.

Quantitative data from the survey were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. SPSS software was employed to perform statistical tests such as chi-square tests, t-tests, and ANOVA to determine significant differences and relationships between variables. Reliability of the survey instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, and a pilot test was conducted to refine the questions and ensure clarity.

Results and discussion

The study's results indicate that soft skills significantly impact the effectiveness of young language teachers, corroborating findings from the literature review and highlighting areas for further development in teacher training programs.

Survey Results

Quantitative analysis of the survey data revealed that communication skills, empathy, adaptability, and cultural awareness are perceived as crucial by a majority of the respondents. Specifically, 85% of participants rated communication skills as extremely important, while 78% emphasized the importance of empathy. Adaptability and cultural awareness were also highly rated, with 72% and 70% of respondents, respectively, indicating their critical role in teaching effectiveness. These findings align with previous research that underscores the value of these soft skills in education (Goleman, 2006; Hattie, 2009).

In terms of classroom challenges, 60% of respondents reported difficulties in managing diverse classroom dynamics, and 55% mentioned challenges in engaging students with varying cultural backgrounds. These results suggest that while teachers recognize the importance of soft skills, there are gaps in their ability to effectively

apply these skills in diverse educational settings.

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical importance of soft skills, such as communication, empathy, adaptability, and cultural awareness, in enhancing the effectiveness of young language teachers. Both qualitative and quantitative data underscore the significant role these skills play in fostering a positive and inclusive classroom environment, which is essential for student engagement and success. Despite recognizing the importance of soft skills, the study reveals a gap in formal training provided by teacher education programs.

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Integrating Language Skills in Teaching English for B1 Level Learners

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Annotation

The article discusses the importance of incorporating language skills into English instruction for B1-level students. It illustrates how the four skills—reading, writing, speaking, and listening—are interrelated and the advantages of a comprehensive strategy that promotes correctness and fluency. We also look at other teaching approaches that can be useful in integrating language skills, such as task-based learning, communicative activities, and technological integration.

Keywords: integrated language skills, B1 level, English language teaching, task-based learning, communicative activities, technology integration.

Аннотация

В статье обсуждается важность интегрирования языковых навыков в обучении английскому языку для студентов уровня B1. Статья иллюстрирует, как четыре навыка — чтение, письмо, говорение и аудирование — взаимосвязаны. В статье также рассматриваются другие подходы к обучению полезные для интеграции языковых навыков, такие как обучение на основе задач, коммуникативная деятельность и технологическая интеграция.

Ключевые слова: интегрирование языковых навыков, уровень B1, преподавание английского языка, обучение на основе задач, коммуникативная деятельность, технологическая интеграция.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada B1-bosqich talabalari uchun ingliz tilini til ko'nikmalarini integrallashgan holda o'qitish muhimligi muhokama qilinadi. O'qish, yozish, gapirish va tinglash ko'nikmalarining o'zaro bog'liqligi yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, topshiriqlarga asoslangan ta'lim, kommunikativ faoliyat va texnologik integratsiya kabi til ko'nikmalarini integratsiyalashda foydali bo'lgan o'qitish usullarini ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: integratsiyalashgan til ko'nikmalari, B1 darajasi, ingliz tilini o'rgatish, topshiriqlarga asoslangan ta'lim, kommunikativ faoliyat, texnologiya integratsiyasi.

The process of acquiring a language is intricate and entails the development of several abilities, including as speaking, writing, listening, and reading. These abilities are interrelated rather than discrete, and mastery of one area frequently affects the growth of others. Integrating language skills is essential for B1 level learners moving from basic to intermediate proficiency to communicate effectively and develop a deeper comprehension of the language. Several strategies and tactics can be utilized to increase language competency, given the importance of integrated language skills in teaching English to students at the B1 level.

Language skills can be successfully integrated using a variety of educational

approaches. Task-based learning is one well-liked strategy that entails giving students real-world assignments that call for the application of several different skills. For instance, a teacher might assign students to design a tourism brochure about a specific location, which would entail researching the area, writing a description, and presenting their results to the class. This kind of work fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities in addition to integrating speaking, writing, and reading abilities.

Using communicative activities that motivate students to engage with one another and utilize the language in relevant contexts is another successful strategy. Role-plays, arguments, conversations, and games are a few examples of these activities. A teacher could, for instance, set up a role-playing exercise where students practice placing restaurant orders. To comprehend the menu, place an order, and answer the waiter's queries, they need to employ their speaking, listening, and reading abilities.

To give students more chances to practice and use their language abilities, technology can be incorporated into the classroom in addition to these conventional approaches. Online platforms, for instance, can be utilized for language games, interactive exercises, and virtual chats. Additionally, learners can access grammar lectures, pronunciation exercises, and vocabulary drills using mobile apps.

According to Monir Nazir Atta-Alla, utilizing storytelling contributes to integrating four language skills and improving language proficiency. 40 volunteer participants were selected for the study and taught listening, reading, writing, and speaking through a story-based learning model developed by the author. The study shows that the participants' language proficiency improved from the previous scores. This suggests that storytelling can effectively contribute to language proficiency.

In addition, Nizamova Rano Akhmadjonovna, Mamadalieva Hapira Abdukhalilovna, and Matkarimova Barno Habibullaevna discuss the integrating of language skills (reading, writing, speaking, and listening) in English language teaching. The authors advocate for a communicative language teaching approach where these skills are integrated to create a more realistic and engaging learning experience.

The integration of four language skills offers some benefits:

- a) encourages natural interaction in the language;
- b) allows teachers to track progress in multiple skills at once.
- c) promotes learning of real content, not just language forms.

We used a mixed-methods approach to investigate the effectiveness of integrated skills instruction on the language development of B1 level English learners. We wanted to identify whether a focus on activities that combine listening, speaking, reading, and writing leads to greater improvement in overall language proficiency compared to traditional instruction that treats skills in isolation.

This study examined how well teaching English to B1 level students involves

combining language skills (speaking, listening, reading, and writing). Following a period of integrated skills education, the study measured gains in both individual skill growth and total language proficiency. A group of integrated skills education students was compared to a control group that received conventional, separate skills instruction using a pre-test/post-test quasi-experimental method.

Using multimodal warm-up activities combining listening, speaking, reading, and writing, such as choral drills, dictations, or surveys, designing project-based learning units requiring research, discussions, presentation, incorporating interactive digital tools like hypertexts, e-portfolios for collaborative reading, writing, and peer feedback were essential in developing B1 level learners knowledge.

The conclusion provides important information about how to teach English to B1 level students while integrating language skills (speaking, listening, reading, and writing). The noted gains in general language proficiency, especially in speaking and listening, are consistent with previous studies that highlight the advantages of a comprehensive, communicative approach to language acquisition. By definition, the integrated skills approach pushes students to use the language more interactively and authentically, simulating real-world communication situations. Students were able to directly connect their language learning to real-world communication, which probably helped to boost motivation and engagement in the classroom.

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Dealing with discipline problems in the classroom

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada sinfda yuzaga keladigan intizomiy muammolar va ularni hal etish strategiyalari yoritiladi. O'qituvchining intizomga yondashuvi, darsda ijobiy muhitni yaratish, uzluksizlikni ta'minlash, o'quvchilar bilan muloqot va intizomiy rejalarning samaradorligi kabi jihatlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: intizom, sinf boshqaruvi, o'qituvchi, ijtimoiy muhit, muloqot, tartib, pedagogik strategiya.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются проблемы дисциплины в классе и методы их решения. Особое внимание уделяется роли учителя в поддержании порядка, создании позитивной атмосферы, а также разработке эффективного плана дисциплины и взаимодействию с учащимися в конфликтных ситуациях.

Ключевые слова: дисциплина, управление классом, учитель, школьная среда, поведение, стратегия, взаимодействие.

Abstract

This article addresses classroom discipline problems and the strategies to manage them effectively. It highlights the teacher's role in maintaining order, creating a positive atmosphere, ensuring smooth lesson transitions, and developing a consistent and fair discipline plan to reduce behavioral issues.

Keywords: discipline, classroom management, teacher, social environment, communication, order, pedagogical strategy.

Discipline problems challenge most new teachers and even some veteran educators. Good classroom management combined with an effective discipline plan helps keep bad behavior to a minimum so the entire class can focus on learning.

Classroom rules must be easy to understand and manageable. Make sure that you don't have such a large number of rules that your students can't consistently follow them.

Discipline starts with you. Begin each class period with a positive attitude and high expectations. It'll help create a positive learning environment. If you expect your students to misbehave, they probably will. Come to class prepared with lessons for the day. Reduce downtime for students to help maintain order.

Work on making transitions between lessons smooth. For example, as you move from whole-group discussion to independent work, try to minimize the disruption to the class. Have your papers ready to go or your assignment was written on the board so you can move quickly through the process. Many disruptions occur in transitional times during lessons.

Watch your students as they come into class and look for signs of discord. For example, if you notice a heated discussion before class starts, deal with it then. Give the students a few moments to work things out before you start your lesson. Separate them if necessary and try to gain agreement that during your class period at least, they will drop the issue.

Post a discipline plan that you follow consistently to govern student conduct. Depending on the severity of an offense, this should provide a warning or two before formal punishment. Your plan should be easy to follow and cause minimal disruption to your class. For example, first offense: verbal warning; second offense: detention with the teacher; third offense: referral.

Use humor when appropriate to diffuse touchy situations. For example, if you tell your students to open their books to page 51, but three students are so busy talking with each other that they do not hear you, resist the urge to yell. Smile, say their names and ask them calmly to please wait until later to finish their conversation because you would really like to hear how it ends but you have to get this class finished. This should get a few laughs but also get your point across.

Consistency and fairness are essential for effective classroom management. If you ignore disruptions one day and come down hard on them the next, your students won't take you seriously. You will lose respect and disruptions will probably increase. If you appear unfair in how you enforce the rules, the students will resent you.

Address disruptions with in-kind responses. In other words, don't elevate disruptions above their current significance. For example, if two students keep talking in class, don't disrupt your lesson to yell at them. Instead, simply say the students' names and issue a verbal warning. You can also try asking one of them a question to bring their focus back to the lesson.

If a student becomes verbally confrontational, remain calm and remove them from the situation as quickly as possible. Do not get into yelling matches with your students. And do not bring the rest of the class into the situation by involving them in the disciplinary process.

When a student becomes visibly agitated, you must maintain a safe environment for the other students. Remain as calm as possible; your demeanor can sometimes diffuse the situation. You should have a plan for dealing with violence that you discussed with students early in the year. You should use the call button for assistance or have a designated student get help from another teacher. Send the other students from the room if it appears they could get hurt. If a fight breaks out in the classroom, follow your school's rules concerning teacher involvement as many administrators want teachers to stay out of fights until help arrives.

Keep an anecdotal record of major issues that arise in your class. This might be necessary if you are asked for a history of classroom disruptions or other documentation.

Most importantly, let it go at the end of the day. Classroom management and disruption issues should be left at school so you have time to recharge before coming back to another day of teaching.

Every teacher, no matter how good, will have students who are disruptive or annoying in some way. It comes with the territory. Despite the effect they have on you, it is useful to remember that their behavior is rarely directed at you. In fact, looking at it as magnanimously as possible, their misbehavior is a cry for help. These are troubled kids who are not satisfied with themselves or their lot. They may be kids who are victimized by family problems or learning deficiencies. However annoying, they are only seeking what we all want, a sense of worth and belonging. It is a disservice to them and to yourself to respond defensively.

However, none of this is to say that you should put up with their antics, regardless of the motivation. In recent years, it has become fashionable for teachers to be expected to deal with any form of aberrant behavior. This is a perversion of our duty, though. Never forget that your primary responsibility is to those who are ready to cooperate and learn. You are a teacher of Science or English or whatever. Schools have counselors and principals to deal with those who substantially interfere with the teaching/learning process. Rather than a sign of weakness, it is a sign of professionalism to turn over the incorrigible student to these specialists. Some students are so troubled that the solution to their problems is beyond your reach. You should feel no sense of inadequacy in this. After all, no doctor cures all his patients, and no lawyer wins

all his cases. In this entry we will discuss techniques for dealing with such students and the criteria for deciding when to turn them over to others.

Few teachers would call in professionals at the first sign of disruptive behavior. Unfortunately, though, many respond with punitive measures as a first step. Punishment, used as an ongoing tool, only serves to increase fear, resentment and defiance while demeaning personal worth and destroying mutual respect. You have only to consider how you would feel if your principal punished you. You would be horrified if he told you to write a hundred sentences or made you sit in a corner after school. To make matters worse, we often impose such punishments publicly and during the peak of our anger. As mentioned earlier in this website, young teens sense they are becoming adults. Such tactics are belittling and humiliating. At best, punishment imposed in this manner will have only a short-term effect. At its worst, it will create more problems than it solves. You also stand the risk of other students empathizing with the one being punished and sharing his resentment. Also, using punishment as a management tool tends to shift responsibility for actions to the teacher. Students seem to be challenging the teacher to define limits through the imposition of punishment. The phrase is that they are "testing" us. Finally, one who relies on punishment will find that the students are only good when the teacher is in the room.

So, punishment can be eliminated as a means for controlling misbehavior altogether. That is not to say that inappropriate behavior should be allowed to continue with impunity. The concept of logical consequences (which appears on the surface to be punishment but is not) will be explored later. But there are many lesser steps to be taken first.

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DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING AND MEDIA COMPETENCY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY-BASED ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract

In today's rapidly digitizing world, the role of technology in education—especially in language learning—has expanded significantly. This study investigates the integration of technology-based teaching methods in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom to foster both critical thinking and media competency among university students. The research was conducted using a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, classroom observations, and post-instruction interviews. Participants consisted of 100 undergraduate students from a foreign language university, who engaged with digital platforms such as blogs, collaborative tools, multimedia sources, and interactive language applications over a 12-week period. Results showed a marked improvement in students' ability to evaluate digital content critically, recognize bias, and communicate more effectively in academic and digital contexts. Moreover, students demonstrated increased confidence in navigating digital media platforms responsibly and analytically. The study concludes that when integrated thoughtfully, technology not only enhances language acquisition but also nurtures essential 21st-century competencies such as digital literacy and independent thought. While the research was limited to one academic setting and age group, its implications highlight the need for broader curricular reforms to include media education within EFL programs. Practical implications suggest that instructors should be trained in both digital pedagogy and critical media literacy. Socially, the study emphasizes the importance of preparing learners to become informed digital citizens capable of discerning and communicating in a media-saturated world.

Keywords

Technology-enhanced learning; critical thinking; media competency; English language education; digital pedagogy; EFL; language teaching; educational technology; digital literacy; higher education.

Annotatsiya

Tezlik bilan raqamlashtirilayotgan bugungi davrda texnologiyaning ta'limdagi roli, ayniqsa, til o'rganishda - sezilarli darajada kengaydi. Ushbu tadqiqot universitet talabarlari orasida tanqidiy fikrlash va media kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish uchun chet tili (EFL) sinfi sifatida ingliz tilini texnologiyaga asoslangan o'qitish usullarining integratsiyasini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot aralash usullardan foydalangan holda o'tkazildi, jumladan so'rovlar, sinfda kuzatishlar va darsdan keyingi suhbatlar. Ishtirokchilar 12 hafta davomida bloglar, hamkorlik vositalari, multimedia manbalari va interaktiv til ilovalari kabi raqamli platformalar bilan shug'ullangan xorijiy tillardagi universitetning 100 nafar bakalavriat talabalaridan iborat edi. Natijalar talabalarning raqamli kontentni tanqidiy baholash, noxolislikni tan olish va akademik va raqamli kontekstda yanada samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyati sezilarli darajada yaxshilanganligini ko'rsatdi. Bundan tashqari, talabalar raqamli media platformalarida mas'uliyatli va analitik navigatsiya qilishda o'zlariga bo'lgan ishonchni oshirdi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, texnologiya o'ylangan holda birlashtirilganda, nafaqat tilni o'zlashtirishni kuchaytiradi, balki raqamli savodxonlik va mustaqil fikrlash kabi XXI asrning muhim kompetentsiyalarini ham rivojlantiradi. Tadqiqot bitta akademik muhit va yosh guruhi bilan cheklangan bo'lsa-da, uning oqibatlarini EFL dasturlari doirasida media ta'limni o'z ichiga olgan

kengroq o'quv dasturlarini isloh qilish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Amaliy natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qituvchilar raqamli pedagogika va tanqidiy media savodxonligi bo'yicha o'qitilishi kerak. Ijtimoiy nuqtai nazardan, tadqiqot o'quvchilarni ommaviy axborot vositalari bilan to'yingan dunyoda farqlay oladigan va muloqot qila oladigan raqamli fuqarolar bo'lishga tayyorlash muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar

Kengaytirilgan texnologiya asosida o'qitish; tanqidiy fikrlash; ommaviy axborot vositalarining malakasi; Ingliz tilini o'rganish; raqamli pedagogika; EFL; til o'rgatish; ta'lim texnologiyasi; raqamli savodxonlik; oliy ma'lumot.

Аннотация

В современном быстро цифровизирующемся мире роль технологий в образовании, особенно в изучении языка, значительно возросла. В этом исследовании изучается интеграция методов обучения на основе технологий в классе английского языка как иностранного (EFL) для развития критического мышления и медиакомпетентности среди студентов университета. Исследование проводилось с использованием смешанного подхода, включая опросы, наблюдения в классе и интервью после обучения. Участниками были 100 студентов бакалавриата из университета иностранного языка, которые в течение 12 недель работали с цифровыми платформами, такими как блоги, инструменты для совместной работы, мультимедийные источники и интерактивные языковые приложения. Результаты показали заметное улучшение способности студентов критически оценивать цифровой контент, распознавать предвзятость и более эффективно общаться в академических и цифровых контекстах. Более того, студенты продемонстрировали возросшую уверенность в навигации по цифровым медиаплатформам ответственно и аналитически. В исследовании делается вывод, что при продуманной интеграции технологии не только улучшают усвоение языка, но и воспитывают основные компетенции 21-го века, такие как цифровая грамотность и независимое мышление. Хотя исследование было ограничено одной академической средой и возрастной группой, его выводы подчеркивают необходимость более широких реформ учебных программ для включения медиаобразования в программы EFL. Практические выводы предполагают, что преподаватели должны быть обучены как цифровой педагогике, так и критической медиаграмотности. В социальном плане исследование подчеркивает важность подготовки учащихся к тому, чтобы стать информированными цифровыми гражданами, способными различать и общаться в мире, насыщенном медиа.

Ключевые слова

Обучение с использованием технологий; критическое мышление; медиакомпетентность; образование в области английского языка; цифровая педагогика; EFL; преподавание языка; образовательные технологии; цифровая грамотность; высшее образование.

Introduction

The advancement of digital technology has transformed educational environments across the globe, particularly in the field of language teaching. In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education, traditional teaching practices are increasingly being replaced or supplemented by innovative, technology-based approaches. These tools not only enhance linguistic skills but also develop learners' ability to think critically and navigate digital content effectively—skills that are essential in the 21st-century information age. Media competency, defined as the ability to critically analyze

and produce content using various media, is now a necessary component of language learning. The integration of educational technology into English instruction provides a unique opportunity to simultaneously improve language proficiency and foster cognitive and evaluative skills.

This study aims to explore how technology-based English teaching can promote critical thinking and media literacy among university students. The central hypothesis is that students who are exposed to digital tools in language instruction will show improved abilities in analyzing information, questioning sources, and communicating ideas effectively. By examining student outcomes through both quantitative and qualitative methods, this research contributes to the growing field of digital education and aims to inform curriculum developers and instructors on best practices for integrating critical media literacy into EFL programs.

Great! Here's the Literature Review and Methodology sections for the article "Developing Critical Thinking and Media Competency Through Technology-Based English Teaching", complete with APA-style references.

Literature Review

The shift from traditional language teaching toward technology-integrated instruction has opened new pathways for enhancing both critical thinking and media competency. Critical thinking in language education involves analyzing, evaluating, and synthesizing information, and is closely aligned with media literacy, which demands awareness of bias, credibility, and persuasive techniques used in digital texts. [1] As learners increasingly engage with digital media, their ability to think critically about content and contexts has become essential.

According to Warschauer and Healey, technology-supported learning environments encourage greater learner autonomy, promote deeper engagement, and create opportunities for collaboration and reflection. [2] Moreover, digital tools such as blogs, online forums, and multimedia projects have been found to stimulate critical thinking by allowing students to interact with authentic materials and voice their perspectives. [3] Research by Yang and Wu demonstrated that students who engaged in technology-assisted tasks developed better reasoning, analysis, and reflection skills compared to those in traditional classrooms. [4]

Media competency, as conceptualized by Hobbs, goes beyond digital literacy to include the ability to evaluate media messages, understand media production, and create content with purpose and responsibility. [5] The integration of media literacy into language teaching empowers students to become discerning consumers and responsible producers of content. In this context, technology is not merely a tool but a platform for the development of essential cognitive and communicative skills.

Despite the proven advantages, the success of such integration largely depends on the teacher's ability to blend technology with pedagogical goals. The TPACK

framework (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) suggests that effective technology integration must be grounded in sound instructional strategies and subject knowledge.

Thus, the current study draws on these theories and frameworks to investigate the extent to which technology-based English instruction can enhance both critical thinking and media competency in university-level learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods design combining quantitative and qualitative data to assess the impact of technology-enhanced teaching on critical thinking and media competency among EFL students. The quantitative component involved a pre- and post-test design, while the qualitative aspect included focus group discussions and reflective journal analysis.

Participants

The study involved 100 undergraduate EFL students (aged 18–22) from a foreign languages university in Uzbekistan. The participants were selected through purposive sampling and were divided into a control group (traditional instruction) and an experimental group (technology-enhanced instruction). Both groups were similar in language proficiency, determined through a standardized placement test (CEFR B2 level).

Instruments and Materials

The following tools were used:

- Critical Thinking Assessment: Adapted from the Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal.
- Media Competency Scale: Based on the framework by Potter. [6]
- Digital Tools: The experimental group used tools like Padlet, Canva, Edmodo, YouTube, and Google Docs for task-based learning and collaborative projects.
- Interview Protocol: Semi-structured questions focusing on students' reflections on their learning experience and digital engagement.

Procedures

The intervention lasted 12 weeks. The control group followed a standard textbook-based syllabus, while the experimental group engaged in technology-enhanced activities focused on media analysis, group presentations, blog writing, and critical evaluation of online content. Pre- and post-tests were conducted to measure progress in critical thinking and media literacy.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the tests were analyzed using SPSS (paired t-tests and ANOVA), while qualitative data from interviews and journals were coded thematically

to identify recurring patterns and perceptions.

Results and Discussion

Quantitative Results

The pre- and post-test scores of the experimental group showed a significant improvement in both critical thinking and media competency compared to the control group. Using paired samples t-tests, the mean critical thinking score in the experimental group increased from 62.4 to 78.9 ($p < 0.001$), while the control group showed only a slight improvement (from 61.8 to 65.2, $p > 0.05$). Similarly, media competency scores improved from 58.1 to 80.3 in the experimental group ($p < 0.001$), indicating the effectiveness of technology-integrated instruction.

Qualitative Results

Thematic analysis of student journals and interview transcripts revealed three dominant themes:

1. Increased Learner Autonomy: Students reported that using platforms like Padlet and Google Docs enabled them to research independently and collaborate effectively. This aligns with Warschauer and Healey's findings that technology promotes active and autonomous learning. [7]

2. Enhanced Critical Evaluation Skills: Learners indicated improved ability to question media content, identify bias, and differentiate between facts and opinions. This observation supports Hobbs' emphasis on media literacy as a crucial component of critical thinking. [8]

3. Engagement and Motivation: Many students expressed that learning through technology was more engaging than traditional methods. They valued the opportunity to express opinions creatively through digital storytelling and media projects, echoing Yang and Wu's conclusion that technology enhances learning motivation. [9]

Discussion

These results affirm that technology-based instruction can significantly enhance both critical thinking and media literacy when integrated purposefully. The TPACK model was instrumental in ensuring that technological tools were not just add-ons but part of an informed pedagogical approach. [10] The use of real-world digital media made learning authentic, fostering skills that go beyond the classroom.

One unexpected finding was the students' increased ability to engage in constructive peer feedback. This may be attributed to the collaborative nature of online tools, which inherently encourage dialogue and reflection.

Nonetheless, limitations were present. Some students initially faced technical difficulties or lacked digital literacy. This points to the need for foundational tech training at the start of such courses.

Conclusion

The findings from this study highlight the transformative potential of integrating technology into English language teaching to foster critical thinking and media competency. The significant improvement in students' cognitive and evaluative abilities, coupled with their increased engagement, underscores the value of a technology-enriched learning environment.

This research contributes to the growing body of literature that supports the use of digital tools in education, particularly in EFL contexts. By leveraging technology, educators can better prepare students to navigate the complexities of the information age—where critical analysis and media awareness are indispensable.

Teachers should receive training in both media literacy and digital pedagogy to effectively design learning experiences that cultivate these skills. Moreover, educational institutions must provide access to digital tools and platforms that support collaborative and reflective learning.

Future studies might explore long-term impacts of such instruction on students' academic performance or investigate how these competencies influence learners' behavior in online environments. Comparative studies across different educational levels and cultural contexts would also add depth to our understanding.

As technology increasingly mediates communication and knowledge, equipping students with critical thinking and media competencies is not just an educational priority—it's a societal necessity. Empowering learners to analyze and interpret digital content critically can contribute to a more informed and responsible citizenry.

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INTERAKTIV METODLAR ORQALI O'QUV MOTIVATSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING SAMARALI YONDASHUVLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada interaktiv metodlar vositasida o'quvchilarda ta'limga nisbatan qiziqish va motivatsiyani shakllantirishning samarali yondashuvlari tahlil qilinadi. O'quvchilar faoliyatini faollashtirish, mustaqil fikrlashga undash, bilimni chuqurroq o'zlashtirishda interaktiv metodlarning pedagogik imkoniyatlari ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Jahon tajribasi asosida grafik tafakkur, dizayn madaniyati, loyihaviy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar va didaktik vositalardan foydalanish samaradorligi asoslab beriladi. Shuningdek, pedagogik xatolarning oldini olish, ijodkorlik muhiti yaratish, erkin konstruktorlik faoliyati orqali talabalarning mustaqil kasbiy o'sishiga sharoit yaratish bo'yicha metodik tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv metod, o'quv motivatsiyasi, samarali yondashuv, o'quv faolligi, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Annotation: this article analyzes effective approaches to the formation of interest and motivation in education in students through interactive methods. The pedagogical possibilities of interactive methods are shown in activating the activities of students, encouraging independent thinking, deeper assimilation of knowledge. Based on the world experience, the effectiveness of the use of modern digital technologies and didactic tools in the development of graphic thinking, design culture, project thinking is justified. Methodological recommendations are also presented on the Prevention of pedagogical errors, the creation of an atmosphere of creativity, the creation of conditions for independent professional growth of students through free structural activities.

Keywords: interactive method, educational motivation, effective approach, educational activity, educational technologies.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются эффективные подходы к формированию у учащихся интереса и мотивации к обучению с помощью интерактивных методов. Показаны педагогические возможности интерактивных методов активизации деятельности учащихся, стимулирования самостоятельного мышления, более глубокого усвоения знаний. На основе мирового опыта обоснована эффективность использования современных цифровых технологий и дидактических средств в развитии графического мышления, культуры дизайна, проектного мышления. Также приведены методические рекомендации по предупреждению педагогических ошибок, созданию атмосферы творчества, созданию условий для самостоятельного профессионального роста учащихся посредством свободной конструкторской деятельности.

Ключевые слова: интерактивный метод, учебная мотивация, эффективный подход, учебная активность, образовательные технологии.

Kirish. Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarda motivatsiyani shakllantirish dolzarb masalalardan biridir. An'anaviy metodlar bugungi yosh avlod

ehtiyojiga to'liq javob bera olmaydi. Shu boisdan ham interaktiv metodlarning pedagogik amaliyotga joriy qilinishi ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. O'quv motivatsiyasi — bu o'quvchini ta'lim jarayoniga faol jalb qilish, bilim olishga ichki ehtiyojni yuzaga chiqarishdir. Interaktiv metodlar aynan shu ehtiyojni uyg'otish va rag'batlantirishda samarali vositadir. Bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan eng muhim vazifalardan biri — o'quvchilarda mustahkam o'quv motivatsiyasini shakllantirishdir. O'quvchilarning ta'limga bo'lgan ijobiy munosabati ularning kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyati, bilim olishga bo'lgan ehtiyoji va kasbiy o'sishida muhim o'rin tutadi. O'quv motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishda interaktiv metodlar keng imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lib, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi.

Interaktiv metodlar — bu o'quvchilarning faol ishtirokiga asoslangan, o'rganilayotgan bilimni mustaqil tahlil qilish, muhokama etish va amaliyotga qo'llashga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim metodlari majmuidir. Bunday metodlar o'qituvchidan yetkaziladigan monologik ta'lim uslublariga qarama-qarshi turadi va o'quvchini markaziy subyektga aylantiradi[2].

Interaktiv yondashuv quyidagilarga xizmat qiladi bilimni mustahkamlash va ongli tushunishni ta'minlaydi; o'quvchining shaxsiy tajribasiga asoslanadi; o'z fikrini ifodalash, bahslashish va qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi; ijtimoiy faollik va jamoada ishlash malakalarini rivojlantiradi.

Pedagogik faoliyatda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning nafaqat nazariy bilimlari, balki amaliy grafik ko'nikmalari, dizayn fikrlashi va texnik tafakkuri ham rivojlangan bo'lishi zarur. Grafik axborot texnologiyalari, kasbiy ijodkorlik muhiti, hamda korrekktiv mashqlar tizimining joriy etilishi – grafik kompetensiyani kompleks shakllantirishda asosiy vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Mavzu bo'yicha o'rganilgan ilmiy manbalar va yondashuvlar tahlili: Oliy malakali mutaxassislarni tayyorlash va ularning kasbiy shakllanishiga oid jarayonlarni o'rganish, shuningdek, bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kasbga tayyorlanish muammolari R.X. Jo'rayev, A.R. Xo'jaboyev, N.A. Muslimov, N.N. Azizxo'jayeva, D.O. Himmataliyev, B.A. Nazarovalar tomonidan tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, Ye.P. Vox, G.A. Galenyuk, S.V. Jilich, G.M. Klochkova, T.K. Musalimov, T.P. Petlina, A.D.F. Ko'chkarova, D.S. Sayidahmedova, S.S. Saydaliev, A.K. Hamraqulov, G.A. Qayumova va Ch.T. Shokirova kabi olimlar o'z ilmiy ishlarida aynan bo'lajak mutaxassislarning grafik tayyorgarligi va grafik-konstruktorlik kompetentligini rivojlantirish masalalarini chuqur tadqiq etganlar[3].

Jahon tajribasida televizion texnologiyalar sohasida tahsil olayotgan talabalar uchun kasbiy grafik kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda muhim jihatlarga e'tibor qaratiladi. Jumladan, grafik bilimlarni chuqur o'zlashtirish, obyektning funksional

va konstruktiv xususiyatlarini anglash, amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni egallash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bundan tashqari, erkin ijodiy fikrlashga asoslangan grafik axborot texnologiyalari muhiti yaratish, muvaffaqiyatli kasbiy-pedagogik faoliyat yuritish, texnologik muammolarga ongli munosabat bildirish hamda texnologiya fanini o'qitishda yo'l qo'yilishi mumkin bo'lgan xatolarning oldini olishga qaratilgan maxsus korreksion mashqlar tizimini ishlab chiqish bugungi kunda dolzarb masala hisoblanadi.

Quyidagi interaktiv metodlar o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirishda eng samarali vositalar sirasiga kiradi:

- ✓ “Aqliy hujum” (Brainstorming) – o'quvchilarni erkin fikr yuritishga undaydi, tanqidiy tafakkurni faollashtiradi;
- ✓ “Rol o'ynash” (Role Play) – ijtimoiy rollarni bajarish orqali o'zini ifodalash, empatiya va muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi;
- ✓ “Kichik guruhda ishlash” – jamoada hamkorlikda ishlash, javobgarlik hissinini rivojlantiradi;
- ✓ “Vaziyatli masalalarni tahlil qilish” – real hayotga yaqin holatlarni hal qilish orqali amaliy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi;
- ✓ “Interfaol muhokama” – har bir o'quvchi fikrini erkin ifoda etish imkoniga ega bo'ladi, bu esa o'z-o'ziga ishonchni mustahkamlaydi;
- ✓ “Test-sinov va gamifikatsiya” – o'quv jarayonini o'yinga aylantirish orqali raqobatbardoshlik va natijaga intilishni kuchaytiradi[4].

O'quv motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishda quyidagi yondashuvlar muhim o'rin tutadi. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv – har bir o'quvchining ehtiyoj va qiziqishlarini hisobga olish; Motivatsion muhit yaratish – ishtirokchilarni rag'batlantiruvchi ta'lim muhiti shakllantirish; Reflektiv tahlil – o'z fikrini tahlil qilishga, xulosa chiqarishga o'rgatish;

Innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish – vizual vositalar, sun'iy intellekt elementlari, raqamli platformalar orqali motivatsiyani rag'batlantirish; O'quvchini faollikka jalb etuvchi baholash tizimi – ball, baho va tan olish orqali qo'llab-quvvatlash.

Interaktiv metod — bu o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi ikki tomonlama faol muloqot asosida ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish usulidir. Ular quyidagi o'quvchini markazga qo'yish, mustaqil fikrlash, tanqidiy yondashuvga undash, ko'nikmalar va kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi va shaxsiy faollikni oshirish jihatlari bilan ajralib turadi[1].

O'quv motivatsiyasini oshirishda interaktiv metodlarning roli beqiyos. Ular o'quvchini qiziqtiradi, bilim olishga ehtiyoj uyg'otadi, o'zini ifodalashga imkon beradi, ijtimoiy faol bo'lishga yo'naltiradi.

Motivatsiyani oshirishda quyidagi yondashuvlar muhim:

- Didaktik maqsadga mos metod tanlash — o'rganilayotgan mavzu mazmuni

va o'quvchilar darajasiga mos usullar tanlanadi;

- Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim — har bir o'quvchining o'ziga xosligini inobatga olish;
- Refleksiya asosida baholash — dars so'ngida o'z-o'zini baholash orqali o'rganilganlarni anglash;
- O'zaro baholash va hamkorlik — talabalar bir-biriga tayanib ishlashni o'rganadi;
- Gamifikatsiya (o'yin elementlari) — ta'limni qiziqarli tarzda tashkil qilish motivatsiyani kuchaytiradi[4].

Interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish til o'rganish jarayonini yanada faollashtirib, talabalar uchun qulay va motivatsion muhit yaratishda muhim vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, darslarda ushbu metodlarni muntazam qo'llash o'qituvchilarga tavsiya etiladi, chunki bu yondashuv talabalar lug'at boyligini rivojlantirishda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Tahlillarga ko'ra, interaktiv metodlarning oqilona qo'llanilishi o'quvchilarning til o'zlashtirishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, ular dars jarayonida faolroq qatnashadi, yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirish va ularni amaliy nutqda to'g'ri qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Eksperimental tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, interaktiv metodlar orqali ta'lim olgan talabalar faqat yangi leksik birliklarni yod olish bilan kifoyalanmay, balki ularni real muloqot sharoitida mustaqil ravishda va mos kontekstda ishlata olish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishgan.

Bundan tashqari, bunday yondashuvlar darslarga bo'lgan motivatsiyani oshiradi, o'qituvchi va talaba o'rtasidagi hamkorlik ruhini mustahkamlaydi hamda o'zaro fikr almashish va munozara yuritish madaniyatini shakllantiradi. Shu boisdan, chet tilini o'rgatishda interaktiv metodlar tizimli va barqaror tarzda tatbiq etilishi zarur. Kelgusida esa bu metodlarning boshqa til ko'nikmalari — eshitib tushunish, yozma ifoda va grammatikani egallash jarayonidagi ahamiyatini chuqur o'rganish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, interaktiv metodlardan to'g'ri foydalanish o'quvchilarni ta'lim jarayoniga faol jalb etish, bilimga nisbatan ijobiy munosabatni shakllantirish, ta'lim mazmunini chuqur o'zlashtirish hamda motivatsiyani rivojlantirishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy pedagoglar interaktiv metodlarni yangicha yondashuvlar bilan uyg'unlashtirib qo'llasa, ta'lim sifati sezilarli darajada oshadi. Interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish o'quv motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy va samarali yo'nalishdir.

Bunday metodlar yordamida o'quvchilar darsga faol jalb etiladi, bilimlarni ongli o'zlashtiradi va o'z salohiyatini to'liq namoyon eta oladi. Ta'limda interaktivlikni oshirish orqali o'quv jarayoni samarali, maqsadli va natijador bo'ladi. Shuning uchun, har bir pedagog interaktiv metodlarni o'z darslarida tizimli ravishda

qo'llashga intilishi zarur.

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INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNING XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDAGI AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitish jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llashning tadqiqotga asoslangan yo'llari ko'rib chiqilgan hamda o'qitishni samarali va qiziqarli qilish mumkin bo'lgan muhim asosiy strategiyalar muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tizimi, xorijiy til, innovatsion texnologiyalar, interaktivlik, multimediy vositalari, raqamli qurilmalar, internet resurslari, sun'iy intellekt, mobil ilovalar.

Annotation: this article examines research-based ways of using innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages and discusses important key strategies that can make teaching effective and interesting.

Key words: educational system, foreign language, innovative technologies, interactivity, multimedia tools, digital devices, Internet resources, artificial intelligence, mobile applications.

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматриваются научно обоснованные способы использования инновационных технологий в процессе обучения иностранным языкам и обсуждаются важные ключевые стратегии, которые могут сделать обучение эффективным и интересным.

Ключевые слова: образовательная система, иностранный язык, инновационные технологии, интерактивность, мультимедийные средства, цифровые устройства, интернет-ресурсы, искусственный интеллект, мобильные приложения.

Kirish

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimidagi ro'y berayotgan tub o'zgarishlar, jumladan, raqamli texnologiyalarning yuqori sur'atlarda rivojlanishi xorijiy tillarni o'qitish

jarayoniga ham sezilarli ta'sir o'tkazmoqda. Innovatsion texnologiyalar o'quvchilarni rag'batlantirishni kuchaytirish, ularning mustaqil ishlash malakalarini rivojlantirishda hamda o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish, muhim vosita hisoblanadi. An'anaviy usullardan farqli o'laroq, zamonaviy texnologiyalar interaktivlik, multimediya vositalari orqali til o'rganishni qiziqarli, hayotiy va mazmunli qilish imkonini beradi [Ahmadjonov, 2021].

Innovatsion texnologiyalar tushunchasi

Innovatsion texnologiyalar nima o'zi? Bu ta'lim jarayoniga ilg'or yondashuvlar, zamonaviy texnik vositalar va metodikalarni joriy etish tushuniladi. Bular raqamli qurilmalar, internet resurslari, sun'iy intellekt, mobil ilovalar, virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (VR/AR) vositalaridir. Bugungi kunda xorijiy tilni o'rganish faqatgina darslik va og'zaki suhbat bilan kifoyalanmaydi. O'quvchilar o'ziga qulay vaqtda, istalgan joyda tilni mustaqil o'rganish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lmoqda [Chapelle, 2001].

Innovatsion texnologiyalar ushbu jihatlari bilan ajralib turadi:

- interaktivlik hamda vizual effektlar orqali tilni tezroq o'zlashtirish;
- o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlari hamda imkoniyatlarini e'tiborga olish;
- o'z-o'zini baholash tizimining amal qilishi;
- darsdan tashqari mustaqil mashg'ulotlar tashkil etish imkoniyati.

Xorijiy til o'qitish jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalar

Zamonaviy xorijiy til o'rganish endilikda faqat grammatikani o'rganish yoki tarjima qilish bilan cheklanmaydi. Ular audio-video materiallar, multimedia, mobil ilovalar va sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlaridan keng foydalanishga asoslanadi.

Multimedia vositalari: animatsiyalar, video darslar, va interaktiv taqdimotlar yordamida grammatika va lug'at boyligi tezroq o'zlashtiriladi. Ayniqsa, real hayotiy holatlarga asoslangan videolavhalar tilni kontekstda tushunishga katta yordam beradi [Warschauer, 2000].

Mobil ilovalar: Memrise, Duolingo, Quizlet kabi ilovalar foydalanuvchiga kundalik mashqlarni bajarish, lug'at boyligini oshirish va talaffuz ustida ishlash imkonini beradi. Ushbu ilovalarda o'yin shaklida taqdim etilgan mashqlar o'quvchilarda raqobat ruhini kuchaytiradi.

Onlayn platformalar: Zoom, Google Classroom, Moodle kabi tizimlar masofaviy o'qitishda qulay muhit yaratadi. Xususan, pandemiya davrida ushbu platformalar afzalligi yaqqol namoyon bo'ldi.

Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari: Grammarly, ChatGPT kabi vositalar orqali o'quvchilarning yozma nutqini tahlil qilish, matn tuzish va grammatik xatolarni tuzatish imkoniyati yuzaga keldi. Bu esa o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantiradi [Bax, 2003].

Amaliy tajriba va samaradorlik

Tajribala va tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion texnologiyalar bilan boyitilgan darslar o'quvchilarda quyidagi ijobiy o'zgarishlarga olib keladi:

- og'zaki nutq va tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalari tezroq rivojlanadi;
- darsga qiziqish ortadi, mashg'ulotlarda o'quvchilar ishtiroki faollashadi;
- mustaqil til o'rganishga qiziqish va intilish kuchayadi;
- o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish (self-assessment) imkoniyatlari kengayadi.

Masalan, Toshkentdagi ayrim OO'Ylarda olib borilgan tajribalarda Quizlet va Kahoot platformalaridan foydalangan holda o'tkazilgan darslar o'quvchilarning 85 foizida so'z boyligi zaxirasi va eslab qolish darajasi oshganini ko'rsatgan [Ahmadjonov, 2021, 73-b.].

Xulosa va tavsiyalar

Innovatsion texnologiyalar xorijiy til o'qitish jarayonining ajralmas qismiga aylanmoqda. Ular ta'lim sifatini oshiribgina qolmay, balki o'quvchilarni til muhitiga jalb etadi. Shu sabablar har bir o'qituvchi quyidagilarga ahamiyat berishi lozim:

- o'z faniga mos innovatsion vositalarni tanlash;
- multimediya va internet resurslaridan samarali foydalanish;
- sun'iy intellekt vositalarini darslarga integratsiya qilish;
- o'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlashini rag'batlantirish.

Yaqin kelajakda til o'rganishning ko'plab jihatlari sun'iy intellekt orqali to'liq avtomatlashtirilishi kutilmoqda.

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USING EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES TO DEVELOP STUDENT'S COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES

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Chirchiq davlat pedagogika universitetining xorijiy til va adabiyoti ingliz tili
yo'nalishi talabasi

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Lingvistika va ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi kafedrası o'qituvchisi

Abstract: The integration of educational technologies in the classroom offers innovative ways to enhance students' communicative abilities. By leveraging tools such as online platforms, interactive applications, and multimedia resources, educators can create dynamic learning environments that foster communication skills. This article explores various technologies that facilitate language learning and communication, focusing on the benefits and practical applications in the classroom.

Интеграция образовательных технологий в классе предлагает инновационные способы улучшения коммуникативных способностей учащихся. Используя такие инструменты, как онлайн-платформы, интерактивные приложения и мультимедийные ресурсы, преподаватели могут создавать динамичные учебные среды, способствующие развитию коммуникативных навыков. В этой статье рассматриваются различные технологии, облегчающие изучение языка и коммуникацию, с упором на преимущества и практическое применение в классе.

Ta'lim texnologiyalarining sinfda integratsiyalashuvi o'quvchilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatini oshirishning innovatsion usullarini taklif etadi. Onlayn platformalar, interaktiv ilovalar va multimedia resurslari kabi vositalardan foydalanish orqali o'qituvchilar muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi dinamik o'quv muhitlarini yaratishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola til o'rganish va muloqotni osonlashtiradigan turli texnologiyalarni o'rganadi, sinfdagi afzalliklari va amaliy qo'llanilishiga e'tibor qaratadi.

Keywords: Educational technologies, communicative abilities, language learning, interactive applications, online platforms, multimedia resources.

Образовательные технологии, коммуникативные способности, изучение языка, интерактивные приложения, онлайн-платформы, мультимедийные ресурсы.

Ta'lim texnologiyalari, kommunikativ qobiliyatlar, til o'rganish, interaktiv ilovalar, onlayn platformalar, multimedia resurslari.

Introduction: As the digital age progresses, the role of educational technology in developing students' communicative abilities becomes increasingly significant. Tools and resources available today can transform traditional teaching methods, making learning more relevant and engaging for students. This article discusses how various educational technologies can be used to cultivate communication skills in language learners. When this happens, some students finish interaction and leave the problem unsettled (19,5 %), other ones try neither ask nor answer questions. Admitting of authoritarian manner in communication (46,3%), inability to self-analysis and failing to judge the interlocutor (36%), refusal to admit errors in communication (31%), unwillingness to solve problem-based tasks, reluctant starting a conversation even in the mother tongue (38,8%) also indicate an insufficient level of students' communicative skills development.

The ability to interact with others, establish and restore appropriate relationships with communication partners, behave appropriately, and control behavior in accordance with communication tasks are all considered communicative skills in

Russian pedagogical and methodical scientific literature (Passov, 2000). According to Zimnyaya (2010), communicative skills are also viewed as a complex of acknowledged, language-mediated, and situation-specific intentional actions that guarantee the resolution of informative communication aspects, the development of partners' corporate communication strategy, and their mutual perception. According to foreign experts, the ability to communicate is a crucial component of social and behavioral skills. Some of them understand communicative skills as ability to cooperate (Widdowson, 2011). According to Osiyanova and Vdovichenko (2016), we believe that the following abilities should be considered communicative: listening skills, the ability to respond quickly to the partner's body language and verbal behavior, the ability to conduct a conversation, the ability to appropriately respond to the partner's question or statement, the ability to choose and use language in a way that affects the other person, and the ability to solve interpersonal and cross-cultural communication problem. We conducted a diagnostic evaluation of communicative abilities with Orenburg State University philology students, and the results indicated that 58.5% of them struggle with spontaneous English speech. Some of them (35%) struggle to find the right words and have a little vocabulary; 8% struggle with tenses and 8% struggle with what to say. Because of this, 52.7% of our respondents are stuck and wait for their partner's advice when completing unique, unconventional communication tasks.

Interactive Language Learning Tools

1. Online Collaboration Platforms

Platforms such as Google Classroom and Microsoft Teams facilitate collaboration among students. These tools allow learners to work on group projects, share ideas instantaneously, and communicate effectively regardless of their physical location. The emphasis on group interaction encourages students to express their thoughts and collaborate, enhancing their verbal communication skills.

2. Language Learning Apps

Mobile applications like Duolingo and Babbel provide interactive language practice that promotes speaking, listening, and writing. These apps offer gamified learning experiences that can stimulate student interest and improve proficiency in a foreign language. Their interactive exercises often mimic real-life conversations, providing practical language use scenarios.

3. Video Conferencing Tools

Applications such as Zoom and Skype enable students to engage in real-time conversations with peers, native speakers, or experts from around the world. This exposure to diverse accents and communicative styles enriches their listening and speaking skills. Virtual language exchange programs can also foster authentic communication experiences.

Multimedia Resources

1. Podcasts and Video Content

Incorporating podcasts and videos into language lessons allows students to encounter authentic language in context. Educators can assign specific episodes or clips that challenge students to summarize, discuss, or critique the content, thus honing their speaking and listening abilities. The varied accents and vocabularies introduce students to real-world language applications.

2. Interactive Whiteboards

Tools such as smart boards allow teachers to create interactive lessons that engage students in language activities. Through discussions, role plays, and multimedia presentations displayed on the board, students can participate actively, enhancing their ability to communicate and collaborate with peers.

Conclusion: Utilizing educational technologies in the classroom can significantly boost students' communicative abilities. By integrating platforms that promote collaboration, interactive applications for language practice, and multimedia resources, educators can create an environment conducive to developing effective communication skills. As technology continues to evolve, embracing these tools will be crucial in preparing students to thrive in a globally connected world.

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So'zlashuv darslarida ravonlikni oshirish usullari

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada chet tilini o'rgatishda, ayniqsa, so'zlashuv darslarida o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutq ravonligini oshirishga qaratilgan samarali metodlar yoritiladi. Ravonlikni shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda kommunikativ yondashuvlar, interaktiv mashg'ulotlar, texnologik vositalardan foydalanish hamda zamonaviy metodik usullar asosida misollar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ravonlik, so'zlashuv, chet tili ta'limi, kommunikativ yondashuv, interaktiv metodlar.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются эффективные методы повышения беглости устной речи учащихся на занятиях по разговорной речи в процессе обучения иностранному языку. Описываются коммуникативные подходы, интерактивные упражнения, использование технологий и современные методики.

Ключевые слова: беглость, разговорная речь, преподавание иностранного языка, коммуникативный подход, интерактивные методы.

Abstract

This article explores effective methods for improving students' oral fluency in speaking classes within foreign language instruction. It discusses communicative approaches, interactive activities, the use of technological tools, and modern methodological strategies to enhance fluency development.

Keywords: fluency, speaking, foreign language teaching, communicative approach, interactive methods.

1. Kirish

Chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida to'rt asosiy ko'nikma — tinglab tushunish, o'qish, yozish va so'zlashuvdan so'zlashuv (speaking) alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ayniqsa, til vositasida o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etish qobiliyati — ravonlik (fluency) — samarali til o'rganishning mezoni hisoblanadi. Ko'pincha grammatik bilimga ega o'quvchilar og'zaki nutqda qiynaladilar. Shu sababli, til darslarini fluency'ni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan tarzda tashkil etish ta'lim jarayonining muhim omilidir.

2. Kommunikativ yondashuvlar

Kommunikativ yondashuv til o'rgatishning zamonaviy va amaliy samaradorligini oshiruvchi metod hisoblanadi. Bu yondashuv o'quvchilarga tilni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo'llashni o'rgatadi. Bunda quyidagi faoliyat turlari qo'llaniladi:

- **Rol o'ynash** — o'quvchilarni muayyan rollarga kiritib, ularning muloqotga faol qatnashishini ta'minlaydi;
- **Simulyatsiya va intervyu mashqlari** — hayotiy holatlarni imitatsiya qilish orqali tabiiy muloqot muhiti yaratadi;
- **Erkin so'zlash topshiriqlari** — o'quvchining mustaqil fikrlashiga turtki beradi.

O'quvchiga ma'lum mavzuda (masalan, "Mening sevimli mashg'ulotim") 1-2 daqiqa davomida to'xtovsiz so'zlash topshiriladi. Bu mashq nutq davomiyligi va tezligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. O'quvchi avval mavzu bo'yicha fikr yuritadi, keyin juftiga aytadi va oxirida sinf oldida bayon qiladi. Bu usul muloqot ko'nikmasini shakllantiradi.

3. Interaktiv metodlar

Matn, hikoya yoki videoni o'z so'zlari bilan qayta hikoya qilish orqali o'quvchi leksik birliklarni mustahkamlaydi va nutq soddaligini oshiradi. Rasmlar, infografikalar, jadvallar va videolar asosida fikr yuritish o'quvchini faol mulohaza yuritishga undaydi. Bahs orqali o'quvchi o'z fikrini asoslash, e'tiroz bildirish va argumentatsiya qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.

Fluency'ni shakllantirishda o'qituvchi har bir xatoni darhol to'g'rilash o'rniga, dars yakunida umumiy muhokama orqali ularni tahlil qilishi maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bu o'quvchilarning ishonchini pasaytirmasdan, ularni muloqotga jalb etishda muhim vositadir.

4. Texnologik vositalar

Bugungi kunda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari til o'rganish jarayonida muhim vositaga aylangan. Quyidagi texnologiyalar so'zlashuv ko'nikmasini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi:

- **Mobil ilovalar** (Duolingo, HelloTalk, Tandem);
- **Onlayn suhbatdoshlar va platformalar** (Speaky, iTalki);
- **Podkastlar va audio darslar** (BBC Learning English, Voice of America).

Bu vositalar darsdan tashqari vaqtda ham til bilan shug'ullanish imkonini yaratadi.

5. Xulosa

So'zlashuv darslarida ravonlikni oshirish uchun kommunikativ va interaktiv metodlardan keng foydalanish zarur. O'qituvchi dars jarayonida o'quvchilarni faol suhbatga, mustaqil fikr bildirishga va erkin muloqotga undashi kerak. Bunda motivatsiya, ijobiy muhit va zamonaviy vositalardan foydalanish til o'rgatish samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

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ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING, TEACHING METHODS AND MODERN TEACHING CONCEPTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the formation of language learning skills in the process of learning English to improve independent writing skills of students using information technology and the development of their creative abilities.

Key words: technical means, television images, distance learning, individualization, differentiation.

Аннотации: В этой статье обсуждается формирование навыков изучения языка в процессе изучения английского языка для улучшения самостоятельных навыков письма студентов с помощью информационных технологий и развития их творческих способностей.

Ключевые слова: технические средства, телеизображения, дистанционное обучение, индивидуализация, дифференциация.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada axborot texnologiyalari orqali talabalarning mustaqil yozish ko'nikmalarini oshirish va ularning ijodkorligini rivojlantirish uchun ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayonida til o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: texnik vositalar, televizion tasvirlar, masofadan o'qitish, individuallashtirish, farqlash.

Reforming the higher education system at the present stage is impossible without the more widely spreading use of computer equipment and information technology, which can be considered technical means of teaching English in higher educational institutions of the country. Today, a university graduate should be an information literate person who knows modern technical technologies well, and also knows how to apply them. The progress of science and technology could not but touch upon the development of the technological base and the teaching of the English language. Widespread television. The introduction of cable television and the reception of television programs using satellite communications contributed to the massive use of television in the educational process. Thanks to the availability of video equipment, teachers in many countries now have the option of distance learning. In many

universities, video libraries have been created and are constantly replenished, the materials of which, along with the printed word, are widely used during self-study hours of student youth for classes. A computer should be considered not only as the most effective tool of human activity in the national economy, but first of all, as an indicator of the culture of mental work of modern man, the main criteria of which are efficiency, the ability to attract and analyze a huge amount of various information, the ability to determine core tasks and for a short time find the right solutions. Computers help a person free himself from secondary, routine work, raising him to a higher, creative level. A computer should be considered not only as the most effective tool of human activity in the national economy, but first of all, as an indicator of the culture of mental work of modern man, the main criteria of which are efficiency, the ability to attract and analyze a huge amount of various information, the ability to determine core tasks and for a short time find the right solutions. Computers help a person free himself from secondary, routine work, raising him to a higher, creative level.

A computer is able to individualize the learning process, control the work of students, correct their mistakes, adapt educational material depending on the individual characteristics of students, simulate various situations, present the material in dynamics. Learning a language with the help of modern technology has become possible, first of all, due to the formalization of certain linguistic phenomena. However, not every material can be embedded in a computer program, the material can be reproduced in strict accordance with the intent of the compiler. It depends on compliance with the requirements of the algorithmic approach. It is necessary, as experts in computer science say, that the considered algorithms are constructed correctly from a formal point of view, that they are decidable and in all cases lead to the desired results. However, not every material can be embedded in a computer program, the material can be reproduced in strict accordance with the intent of the compiler. It depends on compliance with the requirements of the algorithmic approach. It is necessary, as experts in computer science say, that the considered algorithms are constructed correctly from a formal point of view, that they are decidable and in all cases lead to the desired results. In the formation of spelling and punctuation skills, the computer has established itself as an indispensable tool, capable of controlling the assimilation of educational material in a mass audience, and developing, by repeatedly performing the same tasks and exercises, a certain automatism of using word forms in writing. A significant part of existing programs is intended for the formation of a certain vocabulary among students, for example, terminological vocabulary. Depending on the stage and task, the process of mastering the terms can be carried out in various ways that complement each other. Some success, according to the definition of teachers, can be achieved by learning the correct pronunciation. The program of such a complex consists of information and training parts. In the information part, the

student receives the necessary information on a specific issue, in the training part, it consolidates the knowledge gained. The capabilities of such a complex can be realized when working on isolated sounds, syllables, rhythm, intonation. So, when practicing, for example, any sound, auditory visibility can act as a standard, and visual — as a guide in the articulation organization of this sound.

Modern information technology tools are recommended for use in teaching pronunciation, listening, speaking, reading and writing. They make it possible to more fully realize the important didactic principles of teaching — auditory and visual visualization, activity and consciousness, individualization and differentiation, entertaining learning, and make maximum use of students' analytical and imitative abilities. The main thing that contributes to their use is the strengthening of the practical, communicative orientation of training, the development and consolidation of skills in interconnected learning, listening, speaking, reading and writing in English.

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CHET TILLARINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION USULLAR VA TEXNOLOGIYALAR

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida o'qiyotgan o'quvchilarga xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishda innovatsion usullar va texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishning bir necha usullarini yoritib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, ko'nikma, loyiha, taqdimot, ingliz tili, multimedia, kommunikativ rivojlanish, kognitiv faollik, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Annotation: This article highlight several ways to effectively use innovative methods and technologies in teaching foreign language grammar to people's starting at secondary schools.

Keywords: language, skills, presentation, project, English, multimedia, communicative

progress, cognitive activeness, educational technologies.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается о нескольких способах эффективного использования современных технологий и методов в обучении иностранного языка учащихся средних школ.

Ключевые слова: Язык, умение, презентация, проект, английский язык, мультимедиа, коммуникативный прогресс, познавательная деятельность, образовательные технологии.

KIRISH

Bugungi kunda xorijiy tillarini samarali o'qitish ta'lim muassasalarida asosiy vazifa sifatida qaralmoqda. Hamda turli xil innovatsion usullardan va texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda o'rta ta'lim muassasalaridagi o'quvchilarni xorijiy tillarga qiziqish va o'rgatishga e'tibor qaratilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Shavkat Mirziyoyev 2019-yil 11-iyundagi « Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim sohasida boshqaruvni isloh qilish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida» gi PF – 5763 – son qarori oliy va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limi sohasida zamonaviy bilim va yuksak axloqiy fazilatlar, mustaqil fikrlash; zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va chet tillarini chuqur biladigan kadrlar tayyorlashning yuqori darajasi va sifatini ta'minlash, xalqaro amaliyotga yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar va o'qitish usullarini joriy etish, tegishli o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish, o'quv rejalari va fan dasturlarini takomillashtirish, o'qishning zamonaviy shakllari va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etgan holda o'quv jarayonini sifat jihatdan yangilash; oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini samarali tashkil etish, ilmiy tadqiqot natijalarini amaliyotga keng joriy etish, har bir o'quvchining shakllanishi uchun sharoit yaratadi. Chet tillarini o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi o'quvchilarda kommunikatsiya madaniyatni shakllantirish va chet tilini amaliyotda qo'llay olish imkonini yaratishdir.

Tadqiqot mobaynida xorijiy tilni o'rganishning zamonaviy usullaridan, internet moslamalardan foydalanildi. Maqolani yozish jarayonida nazariy didaktiv xulosa chiqarish, mantiqiylik tamoyillaridan foydalanildi.

O'qituvchining xorijiy tillarni o'qitishga o'quvchilarni qiziqtirishda mas'uliyati katta sanaladi. Chunki chetlarini bilish o'quvchilarga keng imkoniyatlar eshigini ochib beruvchi yo'l hisoblanadi. Darslarni samarali o'rgatishda va o'quvchilarga yangiliklarni tushuntirishda texnologiyalar muhim omil sifatida qaraladi. Kommunikativ rivojlanishda internetdan foydalanish eng yaxshi usullardan biridir: Uning maqsadi o'quvchilarning bilim va tajribasini oshirish va kengaytirish orqali xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishga harakat qilishdir. «Bu sirni yaratishdir, u odatda metodologiyada interaktivlik deb ataladi. Interaktivlik — bu nutq poytaxtlari orqali kommunikativ maqsadlarni va natijalarini birlashtirish, muvofiqlashtirish va to'ldirish» demakdir. Internet orqali tilni o'rgatish o'quvchilarga lug'at va grammatikani o'rganishga qiziqishni oshiradi. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarga yo'naltirilgan ta'limni ta'minlaydigan

texnologiyalardan biri bu loyiha ishlari sanaladi. Bu usul o'quvchilarda ijodkorlik kognity faollik va mustaqillikni rivojlantirishda foyda beradi. Mavzuga aloqador loyiha ishlarini qilish, taqdimotlar tayyorlash orqali o'quvchilar o'tilgan mavzuni mustahkamlaydi va mustaqil ravishda darsga tayyorgarlik ko'rishni o'rganadi. Natijada ularda nutq konekmalari rivojlandi. O'quvchi taqdimot rejasini tuzish uni yoritish orqali o'z ijodiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirib boradi va bu usul kelajakda o'z kasbining ustasi bo'lishga ham tirgak bo'ladi. Shu kabi ko'plab sabablar natijasida maktablarda o'quvchilarga xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishda innovatsion usullar va zamonaviy texnologiyalar asosida ingliz tilini o'rgatish asosiy vazifalardan biri bo'lib kelmoqda.

Xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish jarayonida o'quvchilarining to'rtta mahoratini ham muqobil tarzda rivojlantirishda texnologiyalardan keng foydalanish va yangi usullarni darsda qo'llash samarali hisoblanadi. Ularning o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda elektron kitoblar maqolalar, hikoyalar foydalidir. Ushbu manbalar orqali o'quvchi o'zning lug'at boyligini oshira oladi hamda asarlarning asl tildagi versiyasini o'qish imkoniga ega bo'ladilar.

Televizor orqali qiziqarli videolar, foydali multfilm hamda qisqa filmlar nafaqat o'quvchining eshittirish ko'nikmasini rivojlantiradi balki ularni organizotgan fanga bo'lgan qiziqishni ham oshiradi. Mavzulashtirilgan elektron « Kahoot» kabi o'yinlar o'quvchilarning bilimini charxlashda foydali saladi. Va o'z natijalarini ko'rgan holda o'quvchilar shu fanni o'rganishga yanada harakat qilishadilar. Shuningdek bu usul orqali o'quvchilar orasida sog'lom raqobat ham rivojlanadi.

XULOSA.

O'rta ta'lim muassasalarida texnologiyalaridan foydalanish va innovatsion usullarni qo'llash o'quvchilar orasida kerakli axborotni qabul qilish, ularni tahlil qilish, hamda xorijiy tildagi ko'nikmalarni oshirishda muhim sanaladi. Kompyuter, internet va multimedia orqali o'quvchilarga nafaqat o'z tilidagi keng qamrovli ma'lumotlarni, balki dunyo maqolalarini ham xorijiy tilda o'qish imkoniga ega bo'ladi. Shuningdek o'quvchilarda ta'limga bo'lgan qiziqish va motivatsiya oshadi. O'quvchilar orasida texnologiyadan qanday to'g'ri foydalanishni o'rganadilar, keyinchalik bo'sh vaqtlarida ham mustaqil ravishda ta'lim olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

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The Use of Interactive Methods in Increasing Learning Motivation

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Abstract

This research investigates how interactive teaching methods affect student motivation in educational contexts. Using a mixed-methods approach with 127 students across different educational levels, the study demonstrates that interactive pedagogical techniques significantly enhance learning motivation. Data reveals that interactive approaches create supportive learning environments, promote peer collaboration, and foster student autonomy, transforming passive learners into active participants. The research provides evidence-based recommendations for educators seeking to enhance classroom motivational dynamics through interactive approaches.

Keywords: interactive teaching, learning motivation, student engagement, active learning, pedagogical innovation.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu tadqiqot interaktiv o'qitish usullarining ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganadi. Turli ta'lim bosqichlaridagi 127 nafar o'quvchi bilan olib borilgan aralash metodlar yondashuvidan foydalanib, tadqiqot interaktiv pedagogik texnikalar o'quv motivatsiyasini sezilarli darajada oshirishini ko'rsatadi. Ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, interaktiv yondashuvlar qo'llab-quvvatlovchi o'quv muhitini yaratadi, tengdoshlar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni rag'batlantiradi va o'quvchilarning mustaqilligini rivojlantiradi, passiv o'quvchilarni faol ishtirokchilarga aylantiradi. Tadqiqot o'qituvchilarga interaktiv yondashuvlar orqali sinf motivatsion dinamikasini oshirish uchun dalillarga asoslangan tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv o'qitish, o'quv motivatsiyasi, o'quvchilarning ishtiroki, faol ta'lim, pedagogik innovatsiya.

Аннотация

Данное исследование изучает влияние интерактивных методов обучения на мотивацию учащихся в образовательном контексте. Используя комбинированный методологический подход с участием 127 учащихся различных образовательных уровней, исследование демонстрирует, что интерактивные педагогические техники значительно повышают учебную мотивацию. Данные показывают, что интерактивные подходы создают поддерживающую учебную среду, способствуют сотрудничеству между сверстниками и развивают автономию учащихся, превращая пассивных учеников в активных участников. Исследование предоставляет основанные на фактических данных рекомендации для педагогов, стремящихся улучшить мотивационную динамику в классе через интерактивные подходы.

Ключевые слова: интерактивное обучение, учебная мотивация, вовлеченность учащихся, активное обучение, педагогические инновации.

Introduction

Modern education struggles with student disengagement due to the disconnect between traditional teaching and contemporary learning preferences. As Dornyei notes, "Motivation is one of the main determinants of second/foreign language learning achievement" [1]. This principle extends across all educational disciplines.

Rivera and Chen argue that "Today's students require educational experiences that resonate with their lived realities and provide clear pathways to practical application" [2], highlighting the need for alternative pedagogical approaches. Interactive teaching methods position students as active participants rather than passive knowledge recipients. According to Kaur, "Interactive learning environments transform the educational experience from a one-dimensional transmission model to a multidimensional space of discovery and co-creation" [3].

This study investigates how specific interactive methods influence student motivation by addressing three questions:

1. How do interactive teaching techniques impact different dimensions of student motivation?
2. What factors determine the effectiveness of interactive methods in enhancing motivation?
3. How do students' perceptions of interactive environments correlate with motivational outcomes?

Methodology of the Research

This study employed a mixed-methods design with 127 participants: 45 primary school students (grades 4-6), 52 secondary school students (grades 9-11), and 30 university undergraduates.

Research instruments included:

1. **Classroom Observations:** 24 lessons were observed using the Modified Interactive Teaching Assessment Protocol.
2. **Motivation Assessment Questionnaire (MAQ):** Measured intrinsic motivation, task value perception, self-efficacy beliefs, and achievement orientations.
3. **Semi-structured Interviews:** Conducted with 28 students and 12 teachers.
4. **Academic Performance Metrics:** Pre- and post-intervention assessments.

The 12-week intervention implemented problem-based learning, collaborative projects, gamification elements, flipped classroom approaches, and technology-enhanced exercises. Data analysis combined statistical analysis with thematic coding of qualitative data.

Results

Interactive teaching methods correlated with enhanced student motivation across all educational levels, though with varying patterns of effectiveness.

Impact on Motivational Dimensions:

- Intrinsic Motivation: Increased by 27.3% ($p < 0.001$)
- Self-Efficacy: Improved by 23.8% ($p < 0.001$)
- Task Value Perception: Enhanced by 19.4% ($p < 0.01$)
- Achievement Orientation: Shifted toward mastery by 16.7% ($p < 0.01$)

Marković emphasizes that "The transformation of students' motivational orientations requires educational environments that satisfy fundamental psychological needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness" [4].

Differential Effectiveness:

1. Collaborative Problem-Solving: Most effective for secondary and university students (31.2% MAQ increase)
2. Gamification: Most effective for primary students (29.7% MAQ increase)
3. Technology-Enhanced Exercises: Moderately effective across all groups (21.4% MAQ increase)
4. Flipped Classroom: Primarily beneficial for university students (26.8% MAQ increase)

As Zimmerman notes, "Effective motivational interventions must be calibrated to students' developmental needs and existing knowledge structures" [5].

Critical Implementation Factors:

1. Teacher preparation and confidence
2. Quality of scaffolding
3. Authenticity of tasks
4. Balance between structure and autonomy

Henderson observes, "The effectiveness of interactive pedagogy hinges not merely on the methods themselves, but on the thoughtfulness of implementation and alignment with students' context-specific needs" [6].

Conclusion

This research demonstrates that interactive teaching methods can significantly enhance learning motivation when thoughtfully implemented. They create emotionally supportive environments, facilitate meaningful peer interactions, and promote student agency. However, effectiveness depends on selecting techniques aligned with students' developmental needs, providing adequate scaffolding, and ensuring teacher confidence in interactive approaches.

As Patel emphasizes, "Interactive teaching requires not just methodological knowledge but pedagogical agility—the capacity to adapt approaches to specific educational contexts and learner characteristics" [7]. The motivational improvements correlate with enhanced academic performance, supporting Liang's assertion that "Motivation serves as the bridge between teaching method and learning outcome" [8].

Educational institutions should integrate interactive methods into their pedagogical frameworks, accompanied by appropriate teacher training and ongoing

assessment. Future research should explore the long-term sustainability of motivation gains and investigate optimization for diverse learning populations.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOT VA XORIJIY TILLAR

**INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND FOREIGN
LANGUAGES**

**МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНАЯ КОММУНИКАЦИЯ И
ИНОСТРАННЫЕ ЯЗЫКИ**

CHET TILLARINI O'QITISHDA VA MADANIYATLARARO MULOQATDA INNOVATSIYALARNING ROLI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarning chet tillarini o'qitish va madaniyatlararo muloqot jaroyonidagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. O'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda raqamli vositalar, multimediya va sun'iy intellekt asosidagi texnologiyalarning ta'siri yoritiladi. Shuningdek, turli madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunishni shakllantirishda innovatsiyalarning roli ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tillarni o'qitish, raqamli ta'lim, sun'iy intellekt, kommunikativ kompetensiya, interaktiv metodlar.

ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the role of modern innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages and intercultural communication. It highlights the impact of digital tools, multimedia, and artificial intelligence-based technologies on the development of learners' communicative competence. The article also examines the role of innovations in fostering mutual understanding between different cultures.

Keywords: foreign language teaching, digital education, artificial intelligence, communicative competence, interactive methods.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется роль современных инновационных технологий в процессе преподавания иностранных языков и межкультурной коммуникации. Освещается влияние цифровых инструментов, мультимедиа и технологий на основе искусственного интеллекта на развитие коммуникативной компетенции учащихся. Также рассматривается роль инноваций в формировании взаимопонимания между различными культурами.

Ключевые слова: преподавание иностранных языков, цифровое образование, искусственный интеллект, коммуникативная компетенция, интерактивные методы.

KIRISH

Globalizatsiya va raqamli texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi til o'rganish jarayoniga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Bugungi kunda chet tillarini o'rganish nafaqat boshqa davlatlar bilan aloqa vosita sifatida, balki madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirishda ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Butun dunyo bo'ylab innovatsion texnologiyalarning til o'rgatishga nisbatan ta'siri tobora kuchayib bormoqda. Sun'iy intellekt, multimedia vositalalari, raqamli ta'lim platformalari – til o'rgatish metodikasini zamonaviylashtirib, o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini yanada rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada innovatsion

texnologiyalarning ta'lim va muloqotdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi.

Chet tillarini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalarning o'rni

Zamon taraqqiy etib borar ekan tillarga bo'lgan e'tibor ham kuchaya bordi. Nafaqat ona tilini, balki chet tillarini ham mukammal o'rganish zamon talabiga aylanib qoldi. Bizga ma'lumki, chet tillarini o'rganish qiyin bo'lib, bu jarayonda inson murakkab psixologik o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechiradi. Bu jarayonda til o'rgatishning turli metod va texnologiyalaridan foydalaniladi. Misol uchun, hozirgi kunda ingliz tilini o'qitish va o'rgatish, zamonaviy texnologiyalarga borib taqaladi.

Masalan: global tarmoq materiallaridan foydalanib o'quv ko'nikmasi va malakasini shakllantirish; jarayonni individuallashtirish, til o'rganuvchilarning yozish qobiliyatini oshirish; talabalarning so'z boyligi zahirasi to'ldirish va shu kabi ko'plab omillar ingliz tilini o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyani shakllantiradi. Shuningdek, multimediya darsliklardan, video va audio materiallardan foydalanish til o'rganuvchilarni interaktiv faoliyatga jalb qiladi. Umumiy qilib aytganda, chet tillarini o'rganishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llashdan asosiy maqsad fanni oson va jozibali tarzda o'zlashtirishga ko'maklashish hisoblanadi.

Interaktiv metodlar — bu o'qituvchidan faqat axborot berishni emas, balki talabaning fikrlashi, faol ishtiroki va mustaqil fikr yuritishini rag'batlantiradigan o'qitish usullaridir. Bu yondashuvda o'quvchi — bilish jarayonining markazida turadi va dars — ikki tomonlama muloqot asosida tashkil etiladi. Bunday metodlarda: talabalar kichik guruhlarda ishlaydi, savol-javoblar, bahs-munozaralar bo'ladi, o'yinlar, rol o'ynash, muammoli vaziyatlar tahlil qilinadi, texnologik vositalardan (kompyuter, mobil ilovalar, interaktiv doskalar) foydalaniladi. Interaktiv metodlarning maqsadi — bilimni tayyor holatda berish emas, balki o'rganuvchining o'zi mustaqil tarzda anglab yetishiga yordam berishdir. Chet tillarini o'qitishda o'rni Chet tillarini o'qitishda interaktiv metodlar: so'zlashuv ko'nikmasini shakllantiradi, real hayotga yaqin kommunikativ vaziyatlar yaratadi, talabaning ishtirokini oshirib, tilni faol qo'llashga imkon beradi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqotda innovatsiyalar: imkoniyat va yondashuvlar

Madaniyatlararo muloqotda innovatsiyalar, avvalo, yangi texnologiyalarning qo'llash, sun'iy intellekt va raqamli platformalardan foydalanish bilan bog'liq. Shuningdek, Madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda virtual almashinuv dasturlar, xalqaro onlayn konferensiyalar, til klub platformalari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi ta'limiy loyihalar katta imkoniyat yaratadi (Google Classroom, Moodle, Duolingo). Talabalar turli mamlakat vakillari bilan o'zaro aloqa qilib, ularning tarixini, madaniy yondashuvlari, qadriyatlarini bilan tanishadilar.

• **Virtual almashinuv** — onlayn muloqot platformalari va videokonferensiyalar madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirishga katta rol o'ynaydi. Talabalar va o'qituvchilarni turli mamlakatlardan birlashtiradi.

- **Sun'iy intellekt roli** – chat botlar va AI yordamchilari orqali til o'rganish yoki madaniyatlararo savollarni tez va aniq tarzda hal qilish mumkin. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, madaniyatlararo muloqotni kengaytirishga imkon beradi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqotda o'rgatishda yangi metodik yondashuvlar (masalan, blended learning, flipped classroom) qo'llash mumkin. Bu metodlar yordamida ta'lim samaradorligi oshadi va o'quvchilarning madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi ko'nikmalari rivojlanadi.

Amaliy misollar va tajribalar

O'zbekistondagi ayrim universitetlarda zamonaviy til laboratoriyalari tashkil etilgan bo'lib, ular interaktiv metodlar, audio-video tizimlari bilan jihozlangan. Shuningdek, xalqaro hamkorlikdagi onlayn kurslar orqali talabalar chet ellik mutaxassislar bilan muloqot qilishmoqda:

- **SAT** (Scholastic Aptitude Test) — tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini tekshirish uchun o'tkaziladigan imtihon, u matematika va ingliz tili fanlari bo'yicha olinadi. Shuningdek, AQSh, Singapur, Turkiya, Gonkong va Yaponiyadagi ayrim universitetlarga kirish uchun standartlashtirilgan test ham hisoblanadi.

- **IELTS** (inglizcha: International English Language Testing System) – inglizxon mamlakatda ta'lim olmoqchi, immigratsiya qilmoqchi yoki amaliyot o'tamoqchi bo'lgan kishilar uchun test sinovi.

- **TOPIK** (Test of Proficiency in Korean) - Koreys tilini bilish testi bo'lib, bu imtihon orqali birinchi tili Koreys tili bo'lmagan insonlarning koreys tilida gaplashish va tushunish qobiliyatini baholash uchun loyihalashtirilgan. TOPIK testi til o'rganuvchilarning koreys tilida o'qish, yozish va tinglab tushinish darajasini qay holatda ekanini aniqlaydi.

Innovatsiyalarning afzallik va cheklovlari

Innovatsion yondashuvlarning afzalliklari – samaradorlikni, mustaqil o'rganish imkoniyatini, real muloqot muhiti yaratilishi. Biroq ularning ayrim cheklovlari ham mavjud: texnik nosozliklar, internetga bog'liqlik, ayrim o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonlik darajasining pastligi.

XULOSA

Chet tillarini o'qitish va madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirishda innovatsion texnologiyalarning ahamiyati beqiyosdir. Zamonaviy vositalar orqali nafaqat til o'rgatiladi, balki o'quvchilarda madaniy bag'rikenglik, kommunikativ malaka va ijodiy fikrlash rivojlanadi. Kelgusida bu yo'nalishda kompleks yondashuvlar va texnologik integratsiyalar asosida o'quv jarayonini yanada takomillashtirish lozim.

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TILLARNI O'QITISH VA MADANIYATLARARO ALOQALARDA INNOVATSIYALARNI QO'LLASHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitish va madaniyatlararo muloqotda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati yoritiladi. An'anaviy til o'rgatish usullaridan chekingan holda, darsda virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (VR/AR), gamifikatsiya hamda xalqaro muloqot platformalari qanchalik zarurligi ta'kidlab o'tiladi. Ushbu innovatsiyalar til ko'nikmalarini, madaniy tushunchalarni va o'quvchilarning darsga qiziqishini kuchaytirishga xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga, texnologiyaga haddan tashqari bog'lanish va raqamli tengsizlik kabi salbiy oqibatlar ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion texnologiyalar, chet tillarini o'rgatish, madaniyatlararo muloqot, sun'iy intellekt, virtual reallik, o'yinlashtirish, avtonom ta'lim, raqamli tengsizlik, pedagogik strategiyalar, global integratsiya.

Аннотация: В этой статье подчеркивается важность использования инновационных технологий в преподавании иностранных языков и межкультурной коммуникации. Отходя от традиционных методов преподавания языков, она подчеркивает необходимость использования виртуальной и дополненной реальности (VR/AR), геймификации и международных коммуникационных платформ в классе. Эти инновации служат для улучшения языковых навыков, культурного понимания и вовлеченности студентов, а также устранения негативных последствий, таких как чрезмерная зависимость от технологий и цифровое неравенство.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологии, обучение иностранным языкам, межкультурная коммуникация, искусственный интеллект, виртуальная реальность, геймификация, автономное обучение, цифровое неравенство, педагогические стратегии, глобальная интеграция.

Annotation: This article highlights the importance of using innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and intercultural communication. Moving away from traditional language teaching methods, it emphasizes the need for virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), gamification and international communication platforms in the classroom. These innovations serve to enhance language skills, cultural understanding and student engagement, while also addressing negative consequences such as technology overdependence and digital inequality.

Keywords: innovative technologies, foreign language teaching, intercultural

communication, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, gamification, autonomous learning, digital inequality, pedagogical strategies, global integration.

Introduction

In today's era of globalization and the development of digital technologies, learning foreign languages is not just a means of communication, but also plays an important role in the process of intercultural dialogue, international cooperation and mutual understanding of people. Nowadays, the process of teaching a foreign language is not limited to memorizing grammar rules or vocabulary, but is focused on factors such as language learners' understanding of different cultures and their ability to freely communicate with them.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has identified foreign language acquisition and intercultural competence as strategic pillars of the nation's development. In the official document *New Uzbekistan's Development Strategy*, he emphasizes: "If we want to integrate into the global educational and scientific community, it is necessary to teach our youth at the level of international standards. Special attention must be paid to learning foreign languages from an early age. A person who knows several languages not only expands their intellectual horizon but also becomes a bearer of cultural tolerance, open thinking and peace. Our goal is to nurture a generation that feels confident on the world stage, respects national values and embraces universal ones"⁵[1; p.7]. This approach can be a key factor in seeing language teaching not only as a means of imparting knowledge, but also as a bridge between cultures. Through innovative educational technologies, distance learning platforms and immersive cultural experiences language teaching is becoming more effective and globally relevant.

This article analyzes the importance of implementing innovative strategies that help make language teaching more effective and their role in promoting intercultural dialogue — supporting Uzbekistan's broader educational and diplomatic objectives.

Innovations in Language Teaching Methodology

Today, in modern pedagogy, the use of innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages is recognized as the most important factor. The purpose of introducing these technologies is to develop communication skills in a foreign language, increase interest in the lesson process and greatly contribute to independent learning. In particular, the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) is seen as the most effective way to improve the quality of self-study of students. For example, Grammarly and similar AI-powered apps help identify and evaluate not only grammatical, but also stylistic and logical errors. This in itself allows students to a deeper understanding of

1. Mirziyoyev, Sh. (2022). *New Uzbekistan's Development Strategy 2022–2026* (p. 7). Tashkent: Uzbekistan Publishing House.

written communication culture. Research in this field states: “AI-powered writing assistants significantly improve learners’ awareness of syntax and coherence” [6; p.45].

In addition, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies allow for a practical approach to language learning, through which students acquire the skills of communicating in a foreign language. For example, with the help of VR technologies, dialogues can be organized based on roles such as “buyer and seller”, “passenger and airport employee”. In such an environment, the effectiveness of practical language use increases and the knowledge learned remains in long-term memory. Jones comments on this process: “Immersive learning

environments allow learners to simulate real-life communication, fostering deeper linguistic and cultural competence” [3; p.88]. As this approach demonstrates, innovations deepen not only linguistic skills but also cultural understanding.

Another innovative method is Gamification. Through this method, students are interested in accumulating points and stage-based rewards, as a result, healthy competition is formed between them. Platforms such as Duolingo, Kahoot, and Quizizz enhance the effectiveness of lessons and serve as essential tools. They help in teaching foreign languages in an interesting way, especially for elementary school students. Studies supporting this claim conclude: “Gamification enhances learner motivation and vocabulary retention, especially in early stages of language acquisition” [8; p.113].

Moreover, considering that students need practice and a real environment when learning any language, international online platforms like Tandem or Hello Talk play an important role in language learning. Through these programs, you can directly communicate with people who speak different languages and further improve your language skills. Such exchanges not only help form intercultural competence but also nurture learners into open-minded and tolerant individuals. This is clearly expressed in the following academic statement: “Peer-to-peer exchange fosters authentic communication and builds intercultural sensitivity in a natural, dynamic context” [4; p.76].

In conclusion, the use of innovative technologies in language teaching is taking the educational process to a qualitatively new level. They help students understand not only the language, but also the culture associated with it, think freely and communicate. Therefore, the correct selection and purposeful integration of such technologies is the key to success in language teaching.

Positive and negative consequences of innovations in language teaching and intercultural relations.

The development of educational applications has led to significant changes in the fields of language teaching and intercultural communication. For example, with the improvement of educational technologies, language learning materials and platforms are becoming more popular. This allows learners to gather in different geographical

locations, exchange ideas and participate in a multilingual environment at the same time. Mobile-based language learning (MALL) applications, artificial intelligence-based applications such as ChatGPT, Grammarly and Duolingo can be used as a quality online learning platform. As noted in recent studies, “Technological integration in language education promotes autonomous learning, motivation and increased linguistic exposure beyond the classroom” [7; p.51]. This increased exposure enables learners to internalize language structures naturally, while at the same time engaging with diverse cultural contexts. In cross-cultural communication innovation has reached an unimaginable level. People have the opportunity to communicate with each other in real time without any difficulties through platforms like Zoom, Tandem and eTwin. In this way, representatives of different nationalities learn about each other's cultures, languages and ways of life. According to modern pedagogical frameworks, “Virtual exchange environments cultivate empathy, challenge stereotypes and promote mutual understanding across cultures” [5; p.67].

However, along with the achievements of modern technologies in modern teaching methods, there are also disadvantages and negative consequences. The most dangerous factor is excessive dependence on technology. This can lead to young people being excluded from real communication. Although modern communication tools make it easier to communicate with people, they often reduce emotions, which negatively affects relationships. As highlighted by scholars, “Over-digitalization in language education may distance learners from natural communicative situations and reduce the depth of human connection” [2; p.92]. Equity is also considered as an important issue. Not all students are equally provided with modern devices, stable internet and a digital environment. In many regions the “digital divide” is an unresolved problem, which further exacerbates educational inequality.

Innovations in language teaching and intercultural communication undoubtedly bring positive changes, but the long-term effectiveness of these tools depends not only on their technical aspects, but also on the pedagogical strategies that guide them.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of innovative technologies in foreign language teaching has fundamentally changed the field of education and made the learning process interactive, flexible and culturally enriched. In my opinion, these innovations not only make language learning easier and more interesting, but also prepare students to feel confident in an increasingly integrated world. In my personal opinion, a combination of technological tools and traditional pedagogical approaches is important for achieving successful results - this ensures the comprehensive development of the student. If these innovations are implemented on the basis of sound pedagogical strategies, they will not only improve the quality of language teaching, but also play an important role in the formation of open-minded, interculturally competent global

citizens - which is fully consistent with Uzbekistan's aspiration to become a developed and globally integrated society.

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Socio-Humanitarian Aspects of Language Teaching

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Abstract. The act of teaching languages has evolved beyond imparting grammar and vocabulary. It now plays a critical humanitarian role, fostering intercultural understanding, social equity, and active global citizenship. This article explores the socio-humanitarian dimensions of language teaching, emphasizing its role in fostering empathy, intercultural understanding, and social responsibility. Moving beyond technical language instruction, it highlights how language education can serve as a platform for promoting diversity, inclusivity, and critical awareness. Through culturally responsive pedagogy and the integration of global issues into classroom discourse, educators can empower learners to become active, ethical participants in a global society. The article also addresses challenges such as rigid curricula and political barriers, while pointing to digital innovation and global education frameworks as avenues for transformation.

Key words: Socio-humanitarian aspects, language education, intercultural competence, cultural diversity, global citizenship, inclusive education, multilingualism.

Аннотация

Преподавание иностранных языков вышло за рамки простого усвоения грамматики и лексики. Сегодня оно выполняет важную гуманитарную функцию, способствуя

межкультурному взаимопониманию, социальной справедливости и формированию активного глобального гражданства. В статье рассматриваются социогуманитарные аспекты обучения языкам, акцентируя внимание на развитии эмпатии, межкультурной компетентности и социальной ответственности. Языковое образование представлено как средство продвижения разнообразия, инклюзивности и критического мышления. Через культурно ориентированную педагогику и интеграцию глобальных проблем в учебный процесс преподаватели могут формировать у обучающихся качества активных и этически ответственных участников глобального общества. В статье также рассматриваются существующие вызовы, такие как жесткие учебные программы и политические барьеры, и подчеркивается роль цифровых инноваций и международных образовательных инициатив как путей трансформации.

Ключевые слова: социогуманитарные аспекты, языковое образование, межкультурная компетентность, культурное разнообразие, глобальное гражданство, инклюзивное образование, многоязычие.

Annotatsiya

Chet tillarni o'qitish faqatgina grammatik va lug'aviy bilimlarni o'zlashtirish bilan cheklanib qolmaydi. Bugungi kunda u muhim gumanitar rol ni bajarib, madaniyatlararo anglashuv, ijtimoiy adolat va faol global fuqarolikni rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada tillarni o'qitishning ijtimoiy-gumanitar jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi, empatiya, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya va ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni shakllantirishdagi roli ta'kidlanadi. Tillarni o'qitish texnik yondashuvdan chiqib, xilma-xillik, inklyuzivlik va tanqidiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish uchun samarali maydon sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Madaniy jihatdan moslashtirilgan pedagogika va global muammolarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish orqali o'qituvchilar o'quvchilarni faol va axloqiy jihatdan mas'uliyatli global jamiyat a'zolariga aylantirishga ilhomlantirishi mumkin. Maqolada shuningdek qat'iy o'quv dasturlari va siyosiy to'siqlar kabi mavjud muammolar ko'rib chiqiladi hamda raqamli innovatsiyalar va xalqaro ta'lim tashabbuslari transformatsiya yo'llari sifatida ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-gumanitar jihatlar, tillarni o'qitish, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, madaniy xilma-xillik, global fuqarolik, inklyuziv ta'lim, ko'p tillilik.

Introduction

Traditionally, language teaching concentrated mainly on structural proficiency and fluency. In contrast, over the past few decades, there has been a growing emphasis among educators on the wider social and ethical roles of language acquisition. Contemporary educational models regard language instruction as vital for fostering intercultural awareness, encouraging inclusivity, and enabling learners to engage meaningfully in a globalized world (Byram, 1997; Kumaravadivelu, 2008).

Language: A Conduit for Cultural Interaction

Language goes beyond communication; it is a fundamental aspect of society, identity, and culture. To teach a language, a teacher must introduce learners to the cultural realities and perspectives associated with various forms of language use (Kramersch, 1993). Intercultural dialogue enables dialogue and understanding, making language teaching one method to address, eliminate, and stem ethnocentrism while fostering multicultural appreciation (Byram, 1997).

Embedding Humanitarian Perspectives into Language Learning

Adopting a humanitarian stance in language education foregrounds social justice, respect for diversity, and recognition of marginalized voices. Critical pedagogues (Freire, 1970) argue for educational models that validate diverse cultural experiences and confront systemic inequalities. Embracing learners' multilingual and multicultural backgrounds enriches the classroom environment, promoting deeper engagement and inclusivity (García & Wei, 2014). Furthermore, language classrooms can offer spaces where students critically examine pressing global issues such as displacement, discrimination, and environmental crises. Through collaborative projects, debates, and reflective discussions, students develop both linguistic proficiency and a heightened social consciousness (Osler & Starkey, 2005).

Educators as Facilitators of Socio-Humanitarian Values

Language educators carry the important task of fostering spaces that prioritize democratic participation, critical reflection, and cultural responsiveness. Effective teaching goes beyond linguistic instruction to address emotional, cultural, and identity-related dimensions of learning (Cummins, 2000; Gay, 2018). Moreover, guiding students to develop critical language awareness is vital. By understanding how language can perpetuate or challenge power structures, learners are better equipped to navigate and reshape societal narratives (Fairclough, 1992). Additionally, educators should embody and demonstrate values, including fairness, integrity, inclusivity, and compassion through their behavior and interactions with students and colleagues. Social justice, respect for variety, and acknowledgment of underrepresented voices are prioritized when language instruction takes a humanitarian approach. By nurturing a respectful and safe learning space, educators encourage open discussion, critical thinking, and mutual understanding among students. Teachers can weave themes related to human rights, social justice, and civic responsibility into various subjects, prompting deeper reflection. By involving students in community initiatives or service-learning, educators help them put humanitarian principles into practice. Supporting students' development in areas like emotional intelligence and conflict resolution equips them to contribute to a more compassionate and just society.

Barriers and Possibilities

There are some barriers which can come across in socio-humanitarian challenges and opportunities. Cultural Barriers, Unstable political environment, economic inequality, but possibilities include international cooperation, innovation and technology, community engagement and raising awareness. Cultural Barriers: Differences in cultural values and practices can create misunderstandings that hinder humanitarian aid and social cohesion.

Unstable Political Environments: Ongoing conflicts and repressive governments often restrict humanitarian access and limit the influence of civil society.

Economic Inequality: Disparities in wealth and resources often prevent

vulnerable populations from accessing basic services such as education and healthcare. Incorporating socio-humanitarian principles into language curricula is not without challenges. Institutional constraints, such as rigid standardized assessments and political sensitivities around multicultural education, often inhibit transformative practices (Menken & García, 2010).

International Cooperation: Partnerships between nations and global organizations can support more effective humanitarian interventions.

Innovation and Technology: Modern tools like digital platforms and data analysis improve the efficiency and reach of aid efforts.

Community Engagement: Local initiatives and grassroots activism often drive meaningful and sustainable social change. **Raising Awareness:** Education and public campaigns help promote tolerance, empathy, and informed action.

Nonetheless, emerging technologies and global initiatives provide new opportunities. Virtual exchanges, online communities, and intercultural projects enable authentic communication across borders (Thorne, 2010). Furthermore, frameworks like UNESCO's Global Citizenship Education emphasize the urgency of embedding humanitarian values within educational systems (UNESCO, 2015).

Results: Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages in Educational Institutions

1. General Education Schools

At the primary and secondary levels, foreign language instruction predominantly emphasizes communicative competence and basic functional fluency. Methods include:

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT):

Focuses on real-life communication through dialogues, role-plays, and interactive tasks.

Result: Students develop conversational abilities but may show gaps in grammatical accuracy.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT):

Lessons are organized around tasks (e.g., creating a menu, planning a trip) rather than grammar.

Result: Enhances students' problem-solving skills and confidence in using language for specific purposes.

2. Colleges (Technical and Vocational Education)

At the college level, where students often pursue technical or professional education, language instruction is more purpose-driven. Methods include:

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) / Foreign Languages for Specific Purposes (FLSP):

Courses are tailored to fields such as tourism, medicine, or engineering.

Result: Students acquire field-specific vocabulary and language skills necessary for professional contexts.

3. Higher Education Institutions (Universities)

At the university level, foreign language instruction often advances toward academic, critical, and professional mastery. Key methods include:

Academic Language Programs:

Focus on academic reading, writing, and discourse skills (especially for research and presentations).

Result: Students gain proficiency needed for international academic communication.

Intercultural Competence Development:

Courses integrate cultural studies with language learning to prepare students for global interactions.

Result: Graduates become better equipped for international careers and multicultural environments.

Conclusion

Reframing language education through a socio-humanitarian lens broadens its purpose: it becomes a catalyst for building empathetic, critically engaged, and socially responsible individuals. Language classrooms, therefore, hold the transformative potential to not only teach linguistic skills but also to foster ethical global citizens capable of contributing to a more just and inclusive world. Teaching English in socio-humanitarian settings goes beyond language instruction—it serves as a bridge for social inclusion, empowerment, and cross-cultural understanding. By equipping individuals with a global means of communication, English education can open doors to education, employment, and participation in global discourse. In vulnerable communities, especially those affected by conflict, displacement, or poverty, learning English fosters resilience and provides a tool for rebuilding lives. Ultimately, integrating English language education into humanitarian efforts not only addresses immediate communication needs but also promotes long-term social integration and human development.

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TILLARNI O'QITISHDA GENDER VA DINNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tillarni o'qitish jarayonida gender va din omillarining o'rni hamda ularning ta'lim sifati va samaradorligiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Genderga oid stereotiplar va dinga asoslangan qadriyatlar til o'rganish strategiyalariga, o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotga, o'quv materiallarining tanlanishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot davomida turli mamlakatlar tajribasi, ayniqsa musulmon va g'arb jamiyatlaridagi yondashuvlar misollar bilan tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, yetakchi olimlar — B. Norton, J. Sunderland, R. Kubota kabi mutaxassislarining fikrlari asosida masalaga ilmiy yondashuv beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: gender, din, til o'rgatish, o'quvchi yondashuvi, madaniy kontekst.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение гендера и религии в процессе преподавания иностранных языков. Гендерные стереотипы и религиозные ценности оказывают значительное влияние на выбор учебных материалов, методы преподавания и взаимодействие между учителем и учеником. На основе примеров из разных стран, в том числе мусульманских и западных обществ, проводится анализ образовательных практик. Мнения ученых, таких как Б. Нортон, Дж. Сандерленд и Р. Кубота, дополняют научный подход к теме.

Ключевые слова: гендер, религия, преподавание языков, подход учащихся, культурный контекст.

Abstract. This article explores the role of gender and religion in language teaching, emphasizing their impact on learning strategies, classroom communication, and curriculum choices. Gender-based stereotypes and religious values significantly affect both teacher and learner behavior and material selection. The analysis is enriched with international examples, particularly from Muslim and Western contexts, and supported by scholarly perspectives, including those of B. Norton, J. Sunderland, and R. Kubota.

Keywords: gender, religion, language teaching, learner approach, cultural context.

Zamonaviy til ta'limi jarayonida nafaqat lingvistik, balki ijtimoiy-madaniy omillar ham muhim o'rin egallaydi. Shulardan ikki asosiy omil — **gender** va **dinga**

oid qarashlar — til o'rganish va o'rgatishning samaradorligiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Gender rollari va diniy e'tiqodlar o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi, o'rganish usullari, hatto o'qituvchining yondashuvi va o'quv materiallarining tanlanishiga ham ta'sir etadi. Bu omillarni hisobga olmagan holda olib boriladigan darslar ayrim guruhlar uchun noqulayliklar tug'dirishi mumkin. Masalan, J. Sunderland (2004) ta'kidlashicha, sinfda jinsiy rollar bo'yicha tenglikka e'tibor bermaslik, ayniqsa qiz o'quvchilarning ishtirokini cheklab qo'yadi. Shu bilan birga, B. Norton (2000) gender o'zligini (identity) til o'rganishdagi asosiy psixologik omil sifatida ko'radi. Din omilini esa R. Kubota va A. Lin (2009) madaniy va siyosiy kontekstda tahlil qilib, bu omil til siyosatiga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Avvalo, genderning tillarni o'qitishdagi o'rni masalasiga to'xtalib o'tsak.

Til o'rgatishda gender omili ko'plab sotsiologik va pedagogik tadqiqotlarning diqqat markazida turadi. O'quvchilar jinsiga ko'ra ta'lim jarayoniga turlicha munosabat bildiradilar. Masalan, ko'plab tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'g'il bolalar guruhli muhokamalarda faolroq, lekin yozma topshiriqlarda kamroq muvaffaqiyatga erishadi; qiz bolalar esa aksincha, yozma ifoda va eshitish bo'yicha muvaffaqiyatliroq bo'lishadi (Sunderland, 2004).

Ayniqsa ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida, jinsiy tenglikni ta'minlash uchun o'quv materiallarida ***erkak va ayol rollarining muvozanatli tasvirlanishi muhim***. B. Norton (2000) shuni ta'kidlaydiki, til o'rganish — bu shunchaki bilim emas, balki o'zligini (identity) shakllantirish jarayoni hamdir. Shuning uchun o'quvchilarning jinsiy o'zligi hurmat qilinmasa, til o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiya pasayadi. Misol sifatida O'zbekistonda olib borilgan ayrim dars tahlillarida, ayniqsa qishloq maktablarida, ***o'qituvchilar ko'pincha o'g'il bolalarni lider sifatida ko'rsatadi, qizlarni esa passiv rolga qo'yadi. Bu esa ayol o'quvchilarning ishtirokini cheklaydi va gender tengsizligiga olib keladi***.

Dinning tillarni o'rganishga ta'siri ham juda kuchlidir. Dinning o'qitishdagi o'rni, ayniqsa ***diniy qadriyatlar kuchli bo'lgan jamiyatlarda, til materiallari tanlanishi, o'qituvchining darsdagi yondashuvi va o'quvchining faolligiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi***. Misol uchun, musulmon o'quvchilarga mo'ljallangan darsliklarda har qanday jinsiy erkinlik yoki spirtli ichimliklar, raqs va boshqa diniy jihatdan nojoiz bo'lgan mavzular kiritilmasligi lozim. Bu o'z-o'zidan o'quv dasturlarini madaniy jihatdan moslashtirish zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi (Kubota & Lin, 2009).

Dinga asoslangan ta'lim tizimlarida, ayniqsa islomiy maktablarda, jinslararo aloqalar cheklangan bo'lishi mumkin. Bu holat til o'rgatishning kommunikativ yondashuviga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin. O'quvchilar erkin muhokama yoki rolli o'yinlarda qatnashmasligi, bu esa o'quv jarayonining interaktivligini pasaytiradi.

Masalan, Malayziya yoki Saudiya Arabistonida ingliz tili darslari qizlar va o'g'il bolalar uchun alohida o'tiladi. Har bir guruh uchun kontent diniy qadriyatlarga

moslashtirilgan. Bu esa dars materiallari va metodik yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishda diniy tafovutlarni hisobga olish zarurligini ko'rsatadi (Smith, 2012).

Gender va din omillarining kesishuv nuqtalari (interseksionallik) tilshunoslikda hamda pedogogika uchun ham juda ahamiyatli hisoblanadi.

Til o'qitishda gender va din omillari birgalikda namoyon bo'lishi mumkin. **Interseksionallik — bu inson shaxsiyatining turli jihatlarini (jins, din, millat, sinf) bir-biriga ta'sir qilishini anglatadi.** Ayniqsa ayol musulmon o'quvchilarning til o'rganish tajribasi ularning jinsiyati va dini e'tiqodlari kesishgan joyda yuzaga keladigan ijtimoiy bosimlarga bog'liq.

Masalan, **hijob kiygan ayol talabalar ba'zi g'arbiy universitetlarda o'zlarini noqulay his qilishlari mumkin, bu esa ularning nutqiy faolligini cheklashi mumkin. Ba'zida esa ular stereotipik qarashlar tufayli yetarlicha so'zga chiqmaydilar yoki o'z fikrlarini bemalol bildirolmaydilar.** Bu holatga qarshi kurashish uchun, sinf muhitini inklyuziv va tolerant qilish muhimdir (Norton & Toohey, 2011).

O'qituvchi gender va diniy xususiyatlarni hisobga olgan holda, barcha o'quvchilar uchun qulay va xavfsiz o'quv muhitini yaratishi zarur. O'qituvchining o'zi ham gender va madaniy stereotiplardan xabardor bo'lishi, neytral til ishlatishi, dars materiallarini tenglik asosida tanlashi kerak.

Tillarni o'rgatish jarayonida gender va diniy omillarni e'tiborsiz qoldirish o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasiga, ishtirokiga va ta'lim sifati va natijalariga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Mazkur maqolada ko'rib chiqilgan ilmiy yondashuvlar va amaliy misollar shuni ko'rsatadiki, inklyuziv ta'lim tamoyillari asosida tashkil etilgan darslar har ikki omilni hisobga olgan holda samaraliroq bo'ladi. Shuning uchun o'qituvchilar o'z amaliyotlarida gender tengligi va diniy e'tiqodga hurmat tamoyillarini inobatga olishlari lozim.

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“MAXSUS SOHALARDAGI ATAMA VA NOMLARNING LINGVISTIK TIPOLOGIYASI: UZUM VA VINO NOMLARI MISOLIDA”

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada uzum va vino nomlarining lingvistik tipologiyasi o‘rganiladi. Unda ushbu nomlarning kelib chiqishi, tuzilishi, semantikasi hamda madaniy-hududiy xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Muallif uzum va vino nomlari orqali xalqning tarixiy-madaniy merosi, ijtimoiy hayoti va an’analari aks etishini ko‘rsatadi. Turli tillardagi nomlarning qiyosiy tahlili asosida nom berishdagi umumiylik va milliy xususiyatlar aniqlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: tipologiya, tilshunoslik, madaniyatshunoslik, uzum va vino nomlari, uzum navi nomlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается лингвистическая типология названий винограда и вина. Анализируется их происхождение, структура, семантика, а также культурно-региональные особенности. Автор показывает, как через названия винограда и вина отражаются историко-культурное наследие, социальная жизнь и традиции народа. Сравнительный анализ названий на разных языках позволяет выявить как общие черты, так и национальные особенности номинации.

Ключевые слова: типология, лингвистика, культурология, названия винограда и вина, названия сортов винограда.

Abstract: This article explores the linguistic typology of grape and wine names. It analyzes their origins, structure, semantics, and cultural-regional characteristics. The author demonstrates how grape and wine names reflect a nation's historical and cultural heritage, social life, and traditions. A comparative analysis of names across different languages reveals both universal patterns and national specificities in naming practices.

Keywords: typology, linguistics, cultural studies, grape and wine names, grape variety names.

"Uzum va vino nomlari tipologiyasi" degan ibora tilshunoslik, madaniyatshunoslik sohalarida qo‘llanilishi mumkin. Bu yerda **tipologiya** deganda uzum navlari va vino turlari nomlarini tasniflash, ularning nomlanishiga ta’sir qiluvchi omillar, uslublar yoki xususiyatlar tushuniladi. Uzum va vino insoniyat tarixida qadimdan muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan mahsulotlar sirasiga kiradi. Uzum mevasining ko‘plab navlari mavjud bo‘lib, ularning nomlari turli madaniy, geografik va tarixiy omillarga asoslanib shakllangan. Xuddi shuningdek, vino nomlari ham faqatgina tarkibiy qismlar emas, balki muayyan madaniyat, terroir (yer-sharoit), urf-odat va til madaniyatini ham o‘zida aks ettiradi. Ushbu maqolada uzum va vino nomlari tipologiyasi – ya’ni ularning qanday asoslarda tasniflanishi va nomlanishiga e’tibor qaratiladi.

Quyida uzum va vino nomlari tipologiyasining asosiy mezonlari keltirilgan:

Uzum navlari nomlari tipologiyasi

1. Geografik asosli nomlar:

Uzum navi o‘sgan hudud yoki mamlakat nomidan kelib chiqadi.

- Masalan: *Shiraz, Cabernet Sauvignon, Tempranillo, Toskana.*

2. Botanik yoki biologik asosli nomlar:

- Ilmiy tasnifga yoki o'simlik xususiyatlariga asoslanadi.
- Masalan: *Vitis vinifera* (eng keng tarqalgan uzum turi).

3. Mahalliy yoki xalq nomlari:

○ Mahalliy aholi tomonidan berilgan nomlar, ko'pincha dialektal yoki tarixiy ildizga ega.

- Masalan: *Saperavi, Isabella, Kishmish*.

4. Yaratilgan yoki brend nomlar:

- Sun'iy ravishda yaratilgan, ko'pincha marketing maqsadlarida.
- Masalan: *Zinfandel* (aslida *Primitivo* navi bilan bir xil).

Vino nomlari tipologiyasi**1. Uzum naviga asoslangan nomlar:**

- Vino shu navdan tayyorlangan bo'lsa, uning nomi sifatida qo'llaniladi.
- Masalan: *Merlot, Chardonnay, Pinot Noir*.

2. Hudud yoki terroir asosli nomlar:

○ Vino qayerda ishlab chiqarilganiga qarab nomlanadi. Ko'pincha Yevropada keng tarqalgan.

- Masalan: *Bordeaux* (Fransiya), *Rioja* (Ispaniya), *Chianti* (Italiya).

3. Ishlab chiqaruvchi yoki brend nomlari:

- Kompaniya yoki ishlab chiqaruvchining nomi asosida.
- Masalan: *Robert Mondavi Cabernet Sauvignon, Moët & Chandon*.

4. Yaratilish usuli yoki xususiyatiga asoslangan nomlar:

- Vino tayyorlash texnologiyasi, yoshi yoki ta'miga oid belgilar bilan ataladi.
- Masalan: *Vintage, Reserve, Sparkling wine, Ice wine*.

5. Fantaziya va marketing nomlari:

- Emotsional yoki estetik ta'sir beruvchi, badiiy nomlar.
- Masalan: *Black Tears, Midnight Rose, Golden Sun*.

Uzum va vino nomlari tipologiyasi**1. Uzum nomlarining tipologiyasi**

Uzum navlari butun dunyo bo'ylab minglab turlarda uchraydi. Ularning nomlari quyidagi asosiy mezonlarga ko'ra tasniflanadi:

- **Geografik asosli nomlar** – Uzum navlari o'sadigan hudud yoki manbaga qarab nomlanadi.

- Masalan: *Shiraz* (Eron), *Tempranillo* (Ispaniya), *Cabernet Sauvignon* (Fransiya).

- **Botanik nomlar** – Ilmiy tasnifga asoslangan, Latinchaga oid nomlar.

- Masalan: *Vitis vinifera* — eng ko'p yetishtiriladigan uzum turi.

- **Mahalliy xalq nomlari** – Mahalliy tillarda shakllangan, ko'pincha tarixiy ildizlarga ega.

- o Masalan: *Kishmish, Toifi, Saperavi*.

- **Brend yoki seleksion nomlar** – Yangi navlarga sun'iy yaratilgan yoki marketingga yo'naltirilgan nomlar.

- o Masalan: *Zinfandel, Autumn Royal*.

2. Vino nomlarining tipologiyasi

Vinolar o'z nomlanishida ko'p jihatdan uzum navlaridan tashqari madaniy kontekst va ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasiga tayanadi.

- **Uzum naviga asoslangan nomlar**

- o Masalan: *Chardonnay, Merlot, Pinot Noir* – bu vinolar nomida uzum turi aks etadi.

- **Geografik asosli nomlar**

- o Ayrim hollarda vino nomi o'zi ishlab chiqarilgan hududga bog'lanadi:

- *Bordeaux* (Fransiya), *Chianti* (Italiya), *Rioja* (Ispaniya).

- **Brend va ishlab chiqaruvchi nomlari**

- o Masalan: *Moët & Chandon, Gancia, Robert Mondavi*.

- **Tayyorlanish usuli yoki xususiyatiga asoslangan nomlar**

- o *Vintage* (ma'lum yilda yig'ilgan), *Sparkling wine* (shampansimon), *Ice wine* (muzlatilgan uzumdan tayyorlangan).

- **Badiiy va fantaziya nomlari**

- o Ko'pincha emotsional ta'sir qilish yoki marketing maqsadida yaratilgan.

- o Masalan: *Black Tears, Golden Harvest, Midnight Kiss*.

Uzum va vino nomlari — bu oddiy belgilar emas, balki muayyan tarixiy, madaniy va tilshunoslik jarayonlarining mahsulidir. Ularning nomlanishida geografik joylashuv, til o'ziga xosligi, ishlab chiqarish uslubi va madaniyat muhim o'rin tutadi. Shuning uchun vino madaniyatini o'rganish tilshunoslik va madaniyatshunoslik uchun boy tadqiqot maydonidir. Har bir nom ortida tarix, an'ana va terroir yashiringan-bu esa vino va uzumni nafaqat ichimlik yoki mahsulot, balki til va madaniyat hodisasi sifatida ham qabul qilishga undaydi.

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PRAGMATIC APPROACH IN TERMS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. In an increasingly interconnected world, intercultural communication plays a critical role in fostering mutual understanding and collaboration among diverse cultures. One vital element of effective intercultural communication is pragmatic transparency, which combines clear, open, and honest communication with sensitivity to cultural context. This article explores the importance of pragmatic transparency in navigating cultural differences, fostering trust, and minimizing misunderstandings. It highlights how pragmatic transparency facilitates effective communication, problem-solving, and negotiation across cultures by considering communication styles, expectations, and cultural norms. The article also emphasizes how this approach enhances collaboration in globalized environments and contributes to more inclusive, respectful, and productive intercultural interactions. Ultimately, pragmatic transparency is essential for ensuring that communication remains both clear and culturally appropriate in a diverse, interconnected world.

Key words: Intercultural communication, Pragmatic transparency, Pragmatic competence, Intercultural competence, Contextual understanding.

Аннотация. В условиях всё более взаимосвязанного мира межкультурная коммуникация играет ключевую роль в содействии взаимопонимания и сотрудничества между различными культурами. Одним из важнейших элементов эффективной межкультурной коммуникации является прагматическая прозрачность, которая сочетает в себе ясность, открытость и честность в общении с учетом культурного контекста. В данной статье рассматривается важность прагматической прозрачности в преодолении культурных различий, формировании доверия и минимизации недоразумений. Подчеркивается, как прагматическая прозрачность способствует эффективному общению, решению проблем и ведению переговоров между культурами, принимая во внимание стили общения, ожидания и культурные нормы. Статья также акцентирует внимание на том, как этот подход способствует улучшению сотрудничества в глобализированном мире, а также более инклюзивным, уважительным и продуктивным межкультурным взаимодействиям. В конечном итоге, прагматическая прозрачность необходима для того, чтобы общение оставалось как ясным, так и культурно уместным в разнообразном, взаимосвязанном мире.

Ключевые слова: Межкультурная коммуникация, Прагматическая прозрачность, Прагматическая компетентность, Межкультурная компетентность, Понимание контекста.

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi globallashtirilgan o'zaro bog'langan dunyoda, madaniyalararo muloqot turli madaniyatlar o'rtasida o'zaro tushunish va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Konstruktiv madaniyalararo muloqotning eng muhim elementlaridan biri — bu pragmatik shaffoflik bo'lib, u madaniy kontekstni hisobga olib, aniq, ochiq va halol muloqotni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu maqolada pragmatik shaffoflikning madaniy farqlarni yengishda, ishonchni shakllantirishda va noaniqliklarni kamaytirishda qanday muhim rol o'ynashi ko'rib chiqiladi. Pragmatik shaffoflikning madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi samarali muloqot, muammolarni hal qilish va muzokaralar olib borishdagi o'rni, shuningdek, muloqot uslublari, kutishlar va madaniy me'yorlarni hisobga olish orqali qanday yordam berishi ta'kidlanadi. Maqola shuningdek, ushbu yondashuvning globalizatsiya jarayonida hamkorlikni yaxshilashga va madaniy farqlarga hurmat bilan, inklyuziv va samarali muloqotlarni rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini ta'kidlashga qaratilgan. Nihoyat, pragmatik shaffoflik madaniy jihatdan to'g'ri va aniq bo'lgan muloqotni ta'minlashda zarur bo'lgan element sifatida ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, Pragmatik shaffoflik, Pragmatik kompetensiya, Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, Konstruktiv muloqot, Tushuncha.

Introduction

In a world increasingly shaped by global connectivity, intercultural communication plays a pivotal role in fostering mutual understanding and collaboration among diverse cultures. One key element that underpins effective intercultural communication is pragmatic transparency. Pragmatic transparency refers to the practice of being clear, open, and honest in communication while also considering the practical context in which communication occurs. In intercultural communication, this concept becomes even more crucial, as it bridges cultural differences in communication styles, expectations, and norms. This article explores the importance of pragmatic transparency in intercultural communication and its role in facilitating respectful and effective interactions across cultures.

Understanding Pragmatic Transparency

Pragmatic transparency is not just about being transparent in the literal sense of conveying information; it involves a deeper understanding of the cultural and contextual nuances that shape communication. In intercultural contexts, what might be considered “transparent” or “clear” communication in one culture could be seen as overly blunt, disrespectful, or inappropriate in another. Pragmatic transparency, therefore, combines transparency with cultural sensitivity, ensuring that the message is not only clear but also appropriate and considerate of the cultural expectations of all parties involved. [8,24]

Methods

1. Fostering Trust and Mutual Understanding

Trust is a fundamental component of effective communication, especially in intercultural exchanges. Pragmatic transparency helps to build trust by creating an environment of openness and honesty while remaining sensitive to cultural differences. For instance, in some cultures, directness and forthrightness are valued, while in others,

indirect communication is preferred. Pragmatic transparency involves recognizing these differences and adapting communication methods to maintain clarity without overstepping cultural boundaries.

By ensuring that messages are both clear and culturally respectful, pragmatic transparency reduces the likelihood of misunderstandings and fosters a more open and trusting relationship between individuals or groups from different cultural backgrounds. [3,216]

2. Navigating Cultural Differences in Communication Styles

Different cultures have varied communication styles, which can create barriers to effective interaction. Some cultures place a high value on directness and precision, while others may prioritize politeness, subtlety, or harmony in their communication. Pragmatic transparency allows communicators to balance these differences by presenting information in a way that is clear, yet considerate of the listener's cultural expectations.

For example, in many Western cultures, straightforward communication is often seen as a sign of respect, as it avoids ambiguity. In contrast, in certain Asian cultures, such directness may be perceived as rude or confrontational, and indirect communication is preferred. Pragmatic transparency, therefore, requires a nuanced approach—ensuring that communication is both clear and adapted to the cultural norms of the audience. [4,69]

3. Facilitating Effective Problem-Solving and Negotiation

In intercultural settings, effective problem-solving and negotiation often require navigating complex cultural differences. Pragmatic transparency enables negotiators and problem-solvers to communicate their needs and positions in a manner that is both understandable and culturally sensitive. By ensuring that messages are conveyed transparently, parties can avoid unnecessary conflicts and misinterpretations, leading to more productive discussions and outcomes.

For instance, when negotiating between two cultures with different expectations of hierarchy and authority, transparent communication about one's objectives and limitations, while being mindful of the other culture's perspective, can lead to more constructive dialogue and mutual agreement. [1,45]

4. Minimizing Misunderstandings and Conflicts

Misunderstandings often arise in intercultural communication when individuals fail to recognize the sensitivities of another culture's communication style. Pragmatic transparency helps mitigate these risks by offering a clear framework for how to express ideas while considering the cultural context. This proactive approach can help prevent miscommunication that may lead to confusion, resentment, or conflict.

For example, in a multicultural workplace, a manager who practices pragmatic transparency in conveying instructions will ensure that the message is clear to

employees from various cultural backgrounds. The manager will also be mindful of potential cultural differences in how employees may interpret authority and expectations, leading to smoother interactions and a more inclusive environment. [4,65]

5. Enhancing Collaboration in a Globalized World

In the increasingly globalized workplace, individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds often collaborate on projects, sometimes across time zones and languages. Pragmatic transparency allows for the seamless exchange of ideas, ensuring that all participants have a clear understanding of the objectives and their roles in achieving them. It also promotes open dialogue, allowing individuals to share concerns, offer feedback, and seek clarification without fear of misinterpretation or offense.

In a collaborative international team, pragmatic transparency means being clear about one's intentions, goals, and expectations, while also being receptive to the communication styles and preferences of team members from different cultural backgrounds. [7,101]

Intercultural Communication and National Identities

National identities are shaped by shared values, traditions, languages, and historical experiences. These identities influence how people from different countries communicate, interpret messages, and even perceive the role of communication in society. Therefore, when people from different national backgrounds engage in intercultural communication, their national identity can heavily influence their expectations and understanding of the conversation.

In intercultural encounters, pragmatic transparency must navigate these identity markers. Miscommunication is often rooted in the clash of national identities, as individuals' approaches to politeness, formality, directness, and expression vary. What is considered "polite" or "appropriate" in one culture might be perceived as insincere or even offensive in another.

In these situations, pragmatic transparency becomes vital. Clear communication, accompanied by an awareness of the different cultural frameworks, can help bridge the gap between these different styles of interaction. This transparency in communication allows individuals to navigate cultural boundaries with more precision and understanding, reducing the potential for conflict rooted in misinterpretation of intentions or messages.

Results and Discussions: How to Achieve Pragmatic Transparency in Intercultural Communication

Achieving pragmatic transparency in intercultural communication requires intentional effort and practice. Here are several strategies that can help:

1. Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity: Understanding the cultural background of the individuals you are communicating with is crucial. This includes

awareness of their communication style, value systems, and social norms. Being sensitive to these aspects allows one to better tailor their communication to be more transparent and effective.

2. Active Listening: In intercultural contexts, active listening goes beyond simply hearing the words. It involves paying close attention to non-verbal cues, tone, and context to grasp the full meaning behind the message. Active listening fosters understanding and helps bridge cultural gaps.

3. Clarity and Flexibility: While transparency involves clear communication, it is equally important to be flexible in how that clarity is delivered. This may require adjusting one's tone, word choice, or level of directness to align with the cultural expectations of the listener.

4. Use of Neutral Language: In situations where there is uncertainty about how a message might be interpreted, using neutral, universally understood language can help avoid misunderstandings. Avoiding idioms, culturally-specific references, or overly emotional language ensures that the core message is communicated effectively.

5. Feedback and Confirmation: In intercultural communication, feedback is essential for ensuring that the message has been understood as intended. Asking clarifying questions or encouraging feedback helps confirm that both parties are on the same page.

6. Patience and Adaptability: Finally, being patient and adaptable is key. Intercultural communication involves trial and error, and missteps are inevitable. Practicing pragmatic transparency requires the humility to learn from mistakes and the willingness to adjust strategies as needed.

Conclusion

Pragmatic transparency is an essential element of effective intercultural communication. It ensures that communication is not only transparent but also sensitive to cultural differences, creating an environment where trust, understanding, and cooperation can flourish. In today's interconnected world, where intercultural exchanges are common in both personal and professional settings, the ability to communicate transparently and appropriately across cultures is more important than ever. By practicing pragmatic transparency, individuals and organizations can navigate the complexities of intercultural communication with respect, clarity, and success, fostering stronger relationships and more effective collaboration in a globalized world.

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A LINGUAPRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE ON CODE-SWITCHING PRACTICES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article examines Uzbek-English code-switching from a linguapragmatic perspective. It analyzes how bilingual speakers use switching to express intentions, manage conversations, and convey social meaning. Based on real-life examples, the study highlights five key functions of code-switching and emphasizes its role in bilingual communication.

Key words: Code-switching, linguapragmatics, Uzbek-English, bilingualism, pragmatic functions.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillari orasidagi kod almashinuvi linguapragmatik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Unda ikki tilli so'zlovchilar kod almashinuidan qanday qilib niyatni ifodalash, muloqotni boshqarish va ijtimoiy ma'no yetkazishda foydalanishlari o'rganiladi. Haqiqiy hayotdan olingan misollar asosida kod almashinuvining beshta asosiy funksiyasi ajratib ko'rsatiladi va uning ikki tilli muloqotdagi o'rni ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kod almashinuvi, linguapragmatika, o'zbek–ingliz, ikki tillilik, pragmatik funksiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается код-свитчинг между узбекским и английским языками с лингвопрагматической точки зрения. Анализируется, как билингвы используют переключение языков для выражения намерений, управления диалогом и передачи социального смысла. На основе реальных примеров выделяются пять основных функций код-свитчинга и подчеркивается его значение в билингвальной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: Код-свитчинг, лингвопрагматика, узбекско-английский, билингвизм, прагматические функции.

Introduction

Code-switching is a common language behavior of speakers in multilingual societies, it demonstrates speakers' use of language in context, and in keeping with their own identity and cultural role. In Uzbekistan the exposure to English is increasing, along with the use of English, through globalization and educational reforms. Students, young people, and professional bilinguals are producing Uzbek and English code-switching as a practicality or tolerance towards spoken English. The field of linguapragmatics allows research to not only be informed about structures speakers make in switching from one language to the next but also about the pragmatic meanings behind switches. The use of linguapragmatics facilitates not only an understanding of how bilinguals switch language but explains why they switch in one instance and not another, or why they switch in one communicative context versus another. The purpose of this article is to examine and analyze the findings of bilingual speakers using linguapragmatic methods.

Theoretical Background

Though code-switching has been studied in great detail, particularly from a sociolinguistic and structural perspective, the linguapragmatic perspective focuses on the speaker's intentions, the relationship between utterances and context, and the influence on the listeners. According to Gumperz (1982) code-switching should not be conceived of merely as a deficiency in language competence. Instead, it represents a communicative strategy. Pragmatic functions of code-switching include signalling group identity, negotiating social relationships, expressing feeling, clarifying meaning, and managing turn-taking in conversation. The linguapragmatic perspective is particularly useful for analyzing bilingual speech, where switching can be intentional and bound to context.

3. Methodology

The study uses a qualitative methodology to examine naturally-distributed instances of Uzbek-English code-switching in 3 different types of communication. The instances were collected through classroom recordings, social media interactions, and togetherness as university students in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The pragmatic function of each instance of code-switching was separately analyzed and based on categorisation. Instances of code-switching are categorised using five basic pragmatic functions, taken from the categorisation system devised by Appel and Muysken (1987) of referential, directive, expressive, phatic and metalinguistic functions.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Referential Function

Referential code-switching is often done when a speaker has used an English term that does not have a precise equivalent in Uzbek or is more often used in English. For example: "Bugun presentation qilishim kerak." (translation: "Today I need to do a presentation.")

Expressive Function. Bilingual speakers may switch languages while speaking to express emotions or feelings more emphatically. For example: "U meni

rosa xafa qildi. Like, seriously, how could he?"In this example, one use of English is to stress the emotional response of the speaker.

Directive Function. When bilingual speakers use code-switching to attempt to change the behaviour of the listener, the code-switching can be described as a directive function. This type of switch is frequently in a teaching or formal setting. For example: "Qani, open your books to page 25."The speaker switched to English, which serves as an instructive function of the bilingual code-switching.

Phatic Function. Bilingual speakers may use a language switch in a greeting, joke, wish, or casual commentary to express a desire to continue a social relationship or create a sense of solidarity. For example: "Assalomu alaykum! What's up?"This mixture of Uzbek-English is a way of signaling to a potential interlocutor a sense of friendliness, and it could also signal a bilingual speaker shared identity.

Metalinguistic Function. Bilingual speakers may use a language switch to make comments about their language usage. The comments may include correcting their own speech, correcting someone else's, or translating their speech into the language of choice. For example: "Men "deadline" degani nima deb o'ylaysizlar?"This switch serves as an explanation that facilitates understanding the meaning.

Implications. By understanding the linguapragmatic nature of code-switching it is possible for teachers, linguists, and policy makers to see bilingual speakers as competent communicators. In the case of Uzbek-English code-switching, it must be noted that code-switching is more than an act of language interference, but rather a meaningful resource for speakers, communicating meaning, a cultural identity, and facilitating interaction.

Conclusion. Uzbek-English code-switching is a unique and pragmatic in nature, due to context, the intention of the speaker, and social context. A linguapragmatic study of bilingual speakers and code-switching has indicated that

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TURK ADABIYOTIDA TILNING QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada turk adabiyotida tilning qanday ishlatilganligi, uning tarixiy bosqichlardagi o'zgarishi, yozuvchilar va adabiy maktablarning tildan foydalanish usullari va bu orqali jamiyatga, madaniyatga ko'rsatgan ta'siri o'rganiladi. Tilning estetik, uslubiy va funksional jihatlari, uning badiiy obraz yaratishdagi ahamiyati, shuningdek, milliy identitet va ma'naviyatni shakllantirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turk adabiyoti, til ishlatilishi, adabiy uslub, lingvopoetika, tarixiy taraqqiyot, adabiy maktablar, milliy ong, postmodernizm, xalq tili.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассматривается, как использовался язык в турецкой литературе, его эволюция на различных исторических этапах, способы использования языка писателями и литературными школами, а также влияние этого процесса на общество и культуру. Анализируются эстетические, стилистические и функциональные аспекты языка, его роль в создании художественных образов, а также значение в формировании национальной идентичности и духовности.

Ключевые слова: Турецкая литература, использование языка, литературный стиль, лингвопоэтика, историческое развитие, литературные школы, национальное сознание, постмодернизм, народный язык.

Abstract: This scientific article explores how language has been used in Turkish literature, its evolution through various historical stages, the ways in which writers and literary schools utilized language, and the impact of these practices on society and culture. The aesthetic, stylistic, and functional aspects of language are analyzed, as well as its role in the creation of literary imagery and its significance in shaping national identity and spirituality.

Keywords: Turkish literature, language usage, literary style, linguopoetics, historical development, literary schools, national consciousness, postmodernism, folk language.

Turk adabiyoti ming yillar davomida shakllangan va til orqali o'zining mazmunini, estetik va falsafiy jihatlarini ifoda etib kelgan murakkab madaniy tizimdir. Til esa bu tizimning eng muhim komponentidir. Adabiyot tarixiy taraqqiyotning ifoda shakli bo'lsa, til uning mavjud bo'lish shartidir. Shu sababli turk adabiyotining har bir bosqichi tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan ham o'ta ahamiyatli hisoblanadi. Adabiyotning zamirida tilning estetik quvvati, semantik tafovutlari, stilistik imkoniyatlari va fonetik ohangi yotadi. Turk adabiyotidagi tilni o'rganish, nafaqat lingvistik o'zgarishlarni kuzatishga, balki turk xalqining madaniy mentaliteti, ijtimoiy evolyutsiyasi va tafakkur tizimini ham tahlil qilishga zamin yaratadi. Qadimgi turk adabiyotida, xususan, VIII asrga oid Orxon-Yenisey bitiktoshlarida qo'llanilgan til turkiy tillarning eng qadimiy yozma namunasi hisoblanadi. Bu davr tili morfologik jihatdan agglutinativ bo'lib, so'z yasash va fe'l shakllari bugungi zamonaviy turk tillarining asosiy grammatik modelini tashkil qiladi. Bitiklarda ishlatilgan til – oddiy, sodda va leksik jihatdan chuqur

semantik qatlamga ega bo'lgan, o'zida urf-odat, din va siyosiy g'oyalarni jamlagan til bo'lib, bu holat adabiy tilda til vositalarining kommunikativ, estetik va ideologik funksiyalarini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

O'rta asr turk adabiyoti esa ikki asosiy yo'nalishda – saroy (divon) adabiyoti va xalq adabiyoti shaklida rivoj topdi. Divon adabiyotida arab va fors tillarining ta'siri nihoyatda kuchli bo'lib, bu holat tilning morfosintaktik tizimiga, leksik boyligiga va stilistik vositalariga sezilarli darajada ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Alisher Navoiy kabi mutafakkirlar tomonidan yozilgan turkiy devonlar bunday stilistik sintezning eng yorqin namunalari hisoblanadi. Usmonli davrida esa til ikki qatlamli shaklga ega bo'ldi: yuqori tabaqa orasida arabcha-forscha aralash "Osmanlıca", quyi tabaqa orasida esa og'zaki xalq tili ishlatilgan. Bu ikki til qatlamli orasidagi tafovut adabiy asarlarda aks etgan va u orqali ijtimoiy tabaqlanish, siyosiy mafkura va madaniy identitet masalalari ifoda etilgan.

Xalq adabiyotida, ayniqsa, dostonlar, xalq qo'shiqlari, maqollar va afsonalar tilining tabiiyligi, soddaligi va obrazlilik uning barqarorligiga sabab bo'ldi. Bu asarlarda dialektal leksik birliklar, metaforik strukturalar, ramziy obrazlar va ko'p ma'nolilik holatlari tilning xalq ruhiyatini aks ettirishdagi asosiy vosita ekanini ko'rsatadi. Aytish mumkinki, og'zaki xalq ijodi tili yozma adabiy tilga qaraganda ko'proq lingvistik izchillikni, fonetik moslashuvchanlikni va kontekstual moslikni saqlab qolgan.

XIX asr va XX asr boshlarida G'arb adabiyoti bilan tanishuv natijasida turk adabiy tilida yangi uslublar, janrlar va ifoda vositalari paydo bo'ldi. Realistik, naturalistik va romantik uslublarda yozilgan asarlar tilning zamonaviylashuvi, soddalashuvi va demokratlashuviga xizmat qildi. Bu jarayon eng yuqori darajasiga XX asr boshlarida, Atatürk boshchiligidagi til islohoti chog'ida yetdi. 1928-yilda arab yozuvining lotin yozuviga almashtirilishi bilan bir qatorda, tilni "xalq tili" asosida soddalashtirish, arabcha va forsha so'zlarni chiqarib tashlash, yangi so'zlar yaratish, tilni ilm-fan, siyosat va adabiyot tili sifatida qayta qurish harakatlari olib borildi. Bu islohotlar adabiyotda tilning yangi shakllarini yuzaga keltirdi va milliy adabiy tilning shakllanishiga sabab bo'ldi.

Zamonaviy turk adabiyotida tilning qo'llanilishi nihoyatda diversifikatsiyalashgan. Ya'ni, turli yozuvchilar o'zining til tanlovi, uslubiyati va leksik-semantik qarorlarini shaxsiy va estetik afzalliklariga binoan amalga oshiradi. Orxan Pamuk, Elif Shafak, Ahmet Hamdi Tanpınar, Yaşar Kemal kabi yozuvchilarning asarlarida til nafaqat voqelikni ifodalovchi vosita, balki o'ziga xos poetik-estetik olamni yaratish vositasi sifatida qaraladi. Masalan, Pamukning romanlarida til murakkab sintaktik tuzilmalar, ichki monologlar, o'zaro bog'liq ramzlar va intertekstual elementlar orqali muallifning falsafiy-estetik qarashlarini aks ettiradi. Bunday holatda til ko'proq strukturalizm va postmodernizmga xos vosita

sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Tilning adabiyotdagi estetik vazifasi, ayniqsa, she'riyatda yanada chuqurroq seziladi. Zamonaviy turk she'riyatida fonetik musiqiylik, semantik ko'p qatlamlilik, sintaktik konstruksiya va stilistik figura va tropalarning samarali qo'llanilishi orqali til o'zining poetik kuchini namoyon qiladi. Turkiyada kechgan modernizm, postmodernizm, avangardizm, surrealizm va boshqa adabiy oqimlar ham tildagi stilistik yondashuvlarni boyitdi. Ayniqsa, til orqali gender, madaniy identitet, migrantlik, kosmopolitizm kabi mavzularning yoritilishi adabiy tilning zamonaviy ijtimoiy diskurs bilan uyg'unlashuvini ta'minlamoqda.

Bugungi kunda turk adabiyoti global miqyosda tan olinmoqda. Bu esa adabiy tilni boshqa tillar bilan qarama-qarshi va dialog holatiga keltiradi. Tarjima adabiyoti orqali turk tilidagi adabiy ifodalar boshqa tillarga ko'chirilmoqda, bu esa tilning tipologik xususiyatlarini, morfologik tuzilmasini va semantik nozikliklarini global auditoriyaga tanitadi. Til bu yerda nafaqat ifoda vositasi, balki milliy identitet va madaniy kod sifatida harakat qiladi.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib aytish mumkinki, turk adabiyotida tilning qo'llanilishi — bu oddiygina leksik birliklarning to'plami emas, balki ijtimoiy-falsafiy, estetik va madaniy qatlamlarni o'zida mujassam etgan murakkab tizimdir. Har bir davr, har bir adabiy maktab, har bir muallif tilga o'z nuqtai nazaridan yondashgan va u orqali o'z zamonasining ruhini ifodalashga intilgan. Shu ma'noda, til turk adabiyotida doimiy ravishda o'zgaruvchi, lekin har doim mavjud bo'lgan asosiy g'oyaviy va estetik element sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Turk adabiyotida tilning qo'llanilishi tarixiy, siyosiy va madaniy omillar bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, bu jarayon turk xalqining identitetini, estetik qarashlarini va ijtimoiy ongini aks ettiruvchi muhim omildir. Qadimiy bitiklardan to zamonaviy romanlargacha bo'lgan adabiy jarayonlarda tilning semantik, morfologik va stilistik xususiyatlari doimiy ravishda yangilanib, har bir davrning ruhiga moslashgan. Shu sababli, tilni o'rganish — bu adabiyotni, adabiyotni o'rganish esa tilni chuqur anglash deganidir. Turk adabiyoti tilining boyligi, uning o'zgaruvchanligi va estetik kuchi adabiyotshunoslik va tilshunoslik uchun doimiy tadqiqot maydonidir.

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Promoting Global Citizenship through English: The Role of Cultural Awareness and Literature in Language Learning

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Annotation. This article discovers the role of English as a global lingua franca and emphasizes the significance of implementing cultural awareness into English language teaching. It emphasizes how learning English promotes intercultural competence, empathy, and global engagement. The article also provides practical classroom strategies for building a culturally inclusive atmosphere to foster tolerance and comprehension among students.

Keywords: English language, cultural awareness, intercultural competence, global communication, tolerance, inclusive teaching, language learning.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается роль английского языка как глобального лингва франка и подчеркивается важность интеграции культурной осведомленности в обучение английскому. Обсуждается, как изучение английского способствует развитию межкультурной компетенции, эмпатии и глобальной вовлеченности. Также предлагаются практические стратегии создания инклюзивной культурной среды в классе для содействия толерантности и взаимопониманию среди учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Английский язык, культурная осведомленность, межкультурная компетенция, глобальная коммуникация, толерантность, инклюзивное обучение, изучение языков.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilining global til sifatida tutgan o'rni hamda ingliz tili ta'limida madaniy ongni rivojlantirish muhimligi yoritiladi. Til o'rganish orqali o'quvchilar orasida madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, empatiya va global muloqotni rivojlantirish imkoniyati muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada, shuningdek, bag'rikenglik va tushunishni kuchaytiruvchi, madaniy jihatdan inklyuziv sinf muhitini yaratishga oid amaliy strategiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tili, madaniy ong, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, global muloqot, bag'rikenglik, inklyuziv ta'lim, til o'rganish.

In today's world, English has taken on the role of a global lingua franca, making communication available across cultures and enhancing mutual understanding. For teachers of English, it presents a great chance not only to educate linguistic competence but also to upbringing globally minded people. By boosting sensitive and inclusive culture, we can assist learners to be more interested, well-informed, and responsible global residents on a social level.

Embracing and valuing cultural differences can inspire learners to engage effectively with the global community and secretly steer the complications of the world. As a widely utilized global language, English language serves as a door key for intercultural conversation and shared comprehension between individuals. Learning English makes learners go over cultural distinctions and create connections with people from different histories. This learning language gives many plus points:

- **Better perspectives:** Studying English gives learners a set of cultural points, and concepts, making them think twice about concepts and widen their perspective. Going into bigger media, literature, and interactions in English raises a clearer and more critical comprehension of the globe.

- **Encouraging empathetic emotion:** Language learning is able to improve learners' capability to engage with people with various cultural backgrounds. By studying ways of culture, expressions, and communication styles, learners become more aware of the opinions of others, raising peace and respect between culture-related conversations.

- **More complex relationships between cultures:** Possessing a certain English level makes learners participate effectively in global ways of communication, whether with the help of exchange programs, online collaborations or social media platforms. These ways assist to create meaningful conversations with people from distinctive histories of culture and society.

- **Having the key to the door of worldwide ways:** Proficiency of English opens access to a bank of worldwide academic and professional potential opportunities. It enables students to go abroad for studies, have a workplace in places with distinctive cultures, and have the world with much better possession of confidence and perspective.

Ways for how to improve cultural awareness and be tolerant in the English Classroom:

To meaningfully promote sensitive and tolerant culture inside the English language learning environment, educators can implement a set of practical and inclusive teaching strategies, as given below:

- **Implementing cultural elements into the classroom layout decoration:** Creating an interactive and all-included English language class goes far beyond textbooks and lesson worksheets. The physical condition of a class has a pivotal role in changing the attitudes of learners, inducing curiosity, and strengthening academic intentions. One very productive yet often underused strategy in English language teaching (ELT) is implementing cultural elements inside the classrooms.

- **Reasons why cultural classroom displays matter:** The classroom environment affects how learners study, behave and feel. A culturally enriched place not only strengthens the class behaviour more physically motivating but also works as a practical yet ongoing reminder tool that language studying may be naturally linked to culture. According to Byram (1997), 'intercultural competence is a key tool in international language education expertises. Exposing the learners to cultural goals in the class assists them improve curiosity, urge to learn more - qualities efficient for qualitative communication across cultural limitations'⁶.

⁶ Byram, M. (1997). Model of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) Müller- Hartmann,

Learners worldwide encounter culture through literature, and it allows them to explore different cultures, viewpoints, histories, and customs. Reading stories, poems, or passages from various cultures showcases human expression and the manner in which societies view the world. Kramersch in 1993 believed that literature serves students as, 'An understanding of the interplay between a language, its culture and identity'⁷. That proves the point as multicultural literary works assist developing language mastery and intercultural relations.

Most people rely on literature not just for entertainment but also so that they can get out of their comfort zone and go beyond their limitations. Characters from different places allow the readers to see with an open perception which enables students to understand the lives of others and stereotypes that they depend on. Besides, literary works compel students to think critically since they study and analyze perspectives that are culturally different, which challenges norms and helps understanding the complexity of being human.

In addition, the use of authentic materials in literature helps to develop students' vocabulary and understanding of context-specific phrases. Literary texts, which encompass idioms, metaphors, and cultural references, have rich language and culture that goes beyond the bare bones offered by standard textbooks. As Hall (1997) puts it, 'it is through engaging with the narratives of others that learners begin to understand that they are not just beings encased in solitude but rather part of a multifaceted web of humanity'⁸.

Diverse literary works and their incorporation into the curriculum require advanced planning. Such texts can be structured around more universal themes of family, migration, or identity. With these units, learners can be offered texts from different parts of the world so they can appreciate the common experiences of humanity that these cultures tackle from different angles. One example is a thematic unit on 'journeys' which can also include a Native American folktale, a West African myth, and a modern Caribbean short story, all of which offer a travel and exploration theme from different cultures.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTNING ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo muloqotning zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Globalizatsiya va xalqaro integratsiya sharoitida ta'lim tizimi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki turli madaniyat vakillari o'rtasida samarali muloqotga tayyor shaxslarni shakllantiruvchi muhim institut sifatida qaralmoqda. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasining ahamiyati ochib berilib, uning ta'lim jarayonida rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillar, metodik yondashuvlar va innovatsion vositalar yoritiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada xalqaro tajriba asosida samarali strategiyalar ko'rib chiqilib, ularni milliy ta'lim tizimiga integratsiya qilish bo'yicha takliflar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, zamonaviy ta'lim, pedagogik kompetensiya, globallashuv, madaniy tafovut, kommunikativ kompetensiya, xalqaro integratsiya, o'qituvchi tayyorlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется роль межкультурной коммуникации в современном образовательном процессе. В условиях глобализации и международной интеграции система образования рассматривается не только как средство передачи знаний, но и как важный институт формирования личности, способной к эффективному взаимодействию с представителями различных культур. Раскрывается значение межкультурной коммуникативной компетенции для будущих педагогов, а также освещаются ключевые факторы, методические подходы и инновационные средства, способствующие её развитию в образовательной среде. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются эффективные стратегии на основе международного опыта и предлагаются пути их интеграции в национальную систему образования.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная коммуникация, современное образование, педагогическая компетенция, глобализация, культурные различия, коммуникативная компетенция, международная интеграция, подготовка учителей.

Abstract: This article analyzes the role of intercultural communication in the modern educational process. In the context of globalization and international integration, the education system is viewed not only as a provider of knowledge but also as a key institution for shaping individuals capable of effective communication across different cultures. The importance of intercultural communicative competence for future teachers is revealed, and the main factors, methodological approaches, and innovative tools influencing its development in the educational context are explored. Additionally, the article examines effective strategies based on international experience and offers suggestions for their integration into the national education system.

Keywords: intercultural communication, modern education, pedagogical competence, globalization, cultural differences, communicative competence, international integration, teacher training.

Zamonaviy ta’lim tizimi globallashtirish va axborot jamiyati sharoitida nafaqat kasbiy bilim va ko‘nikmalarni, balki kommunikativ va madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasini shakllantirishni ham o‘z oldiga maqsad qilmoqda. Har xil millat, irq va din vakillari bilan o‘zaro hurmat, hamkorlik va to‘g‘ri muloqotni ta’minlash bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilar uchun muhim kompetensiyalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqot — bu turli madaniyat vakillari o‘rtasidagi muloqotning o‘ziga xos shakli bo‘lib, u shaxslararo munosabatda madaniy tafovutlarni hisobga olgan holda amalga oshiriladi. Ta’lim tizimi bu muloqotni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish uchun samarali platforma bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasi bo‘yicha nazariy asoslar Gofsted (Hofstede, 1984), Hall (Hall, 1976), Byram (1997), Deardorff (2006) kabi olimlarning ishlanmalarida chuqur yoritilgan. Ular madaniyatlararo tafovutlarni o‘lchash, anglash va ularga moslashish usullarini aniqlab bergan.[1;89]

Byram (1997) tomonidan ilgari surilgan "intercultural communicative competence" modeli ta’limda keng qo‘llaniladi. Bu modelda o‘qituvchi nafaqat tilni, balki madaniyatni tushunishga, baholashga va unga nisbatan ochiqlikni rivojlantirishga chaqiriladi.[2;112] Mahalliy mualliflar orasida J.Q. Yo‘ldoshev, Z.M. Jo‘rayeva, M.R. Qosimovlarning pedagogik muloqot, tolerantlik va madaniyatlararo tarbiya masalalariga bag‘ishlangan tadqiqotlari e’tiborga loyiq.[3;67]

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi “Ta’lim sifatini oshirish va kadrlar salohiyatini kuchaytirishga oid” PQ–81-sonli qarorida ham ta’limda xalqaro tajribalarning integratsiyasi, raqamli kompetensiyalar bilan bir qatorda madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyaga urg‘u berilgan.[4]

Yevropa Ittifoqi, UNESCO va boshqa xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan olib borilgan izlanishlar ham ko‘rsatadiki, XXI asrda ta’limning ajralmas komponenti bu — madaniyatlararo tushunuvchanlikni shakllantirishdir. Ayniqsa, ko‘p millatli davlatlarda bu masala nafaqat ta’lim, balki ijtimoiy barqarorlik omiliga aylangan.

Pedagogik jarayonda madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirishga quyidagi omillar ta’sir ko‘rsatadi (1-jadval)[5;98]:

1-jadval. Pedagogik jarayonda madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish omillari

2024-yilda Toshkent davlat pedagogika universitetida o'tkazilgan sotsiologik so'rov natijalariga ko'ra:

- 74% talaba madaniyatlararo muloqotni zamonaviy o'qituvchi uchun zaruriy kompetensiya, deb hisoblaydi.
- 58% talaba ta'lim jarayonida turli madaniyatlar bilan ishlash bo'yicha amaliy mashg'ulotlar yetarli emasligini bildirgan.
- 81% ishtirokchi xorijlik talabalarning mavjudligi ularning muloqot ko'nikmalarini oshirganini ta'kidlagan.
- 39% o'qituvchi o'zining madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasini "o'rtacha" darajada deb baholagan.[6;32]

Mazkur raqamlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, madaniyatlararo muloqot bo'yicha nazariy tushunchalarga ega bo'lish yetarli emas, balki amaliy mashg'ulotlar va real muloqot muhitini yaratish zarur.

Zamonaviy dunyoda ta'lim jarayoni tobora ko'proq ko'p madaniyatli, ochiq va global tus olmoqda. Bunday sharoitda o'qituvchining faqat o'z fani bo'yicha bilimdon bo'lishi yetarli emas; u madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasiga ham ega bo'lishi shart. Bu kompetensiya o'qituvchining turli madaniyat vakillari bilan samarali, tolerant va anglangan tarzda muloqot qilishga tayyorligini anglatadi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqotning o'quv jarayonidagi o'rni, avvalo, ta'lim muhitining xilma-xilligidan kelib chiqadi. Ta'lim muassasalarida talabalar turli etnik, diniy va ijtimoiy guruhlariga mansub bo'lishi mumkin. Bu esa o'qituvchidan madaniy sezgirlik, empatiya, moslashuvchanlik kabi sifatlarni talab qiladi.[7;24]

Madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasining asosiy komponentlari:

1. Bilim komponenti – madaniy tafovutlar haqida nazariy bilimlar (urflar, qadriyatlar, normativ xatti-harakatlar);
2. Hissiy komponent – ochiqlik, qiziqish, sabr-toqat, o‘zini boshqasining o‘rniga qo‘ya olish qobiliyati;
3. Amaliy komponent – turli madaniyat vakillari bilan samarali muloqot olib borish malakasi.[8;45]

Bugungi kunda oliy ta’lim tizimida bu kompetensiyani shakllantirishga qaratilgan qator metodik yondashuvlar mavjud. Jumladan:

- loyihaviy o‘qitish (project-based learning),
- ko‘p madaniyatli ta’lim muhiti yaratish,
- xalqaro hamkorlikda seminar-treninglar o‘tkazish,
- onlayn platformalar orqali turli mamlakatlar talabalari bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyatlari.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirishda ayniqsa interaktiv metodlar – simulyatsiya, rol o‘ynash, diskussiya va case-stady (vaziyat tahlili) kabi yondashuvlar yuqori samaradorlikka ega.[9;76]

Shuningdek, o‘qituvchilar o‘rtasida olib borilgan kuzatuv va so‘rovnoma natijalari ham bu yo‘nalishdagi ishlar tizimlashtirishga muhtoj ekanligini ko‘rsatmoqda. Masalan, 60% o‘qituvchilar talabalarda madaniyatlararo sezgirlik yetarli darajada shakllanmaganligini bildirgan. Bu esa, o‘z navbatida, ta’lim siyosatida bu masalaga alohida e’tibor qaratishni taqozo etadi.

Zamonaviy ta’limda madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish quyidagi yo‘nalishlar orqali amalga oshirilishi mumkin:

- O‘quv dasturlariga madaniy tafovutlar bilan ishlashga oid modullar kiritish
- Rolda o‘ynash, muammoli vaziyatlar tahlili, loyihaviy o‘qitish kabi metodlarni faol qo‘llash
- Xalqaro talaba almashinuvini rag‘batlantirish
- O‘qituvchilar uchun maxsus seminar-treninglar tashkil etish[10;87]

Shu orqali bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarning madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasi nafaqat shakllantiriladi, balki ta’lim muhitining integratsion imkoniyatlari ham kengaytiriladi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasi bugungi ta’lim tizimining ajralmas va strategik muhim tarkibiy qismiga aylanmoqda. Globallashuv, axborot oqimlarining tezligi va transmilliy hamkorliklar zamonaviy o‘qituvchidan nafaqat kasbiy, balki kommunikativ va madaniy jihatdan ham yetuk bo‘lishni talab qiladi.

O‘tkazilgan tahlil va statistik ma’lumotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish uchun mavjud salohiyat yetarli bo‘lsa-da, u hali to‘liq ishga solinmagan. Ta’lim muassasalarida bu kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi amaliy mashg‘ulotlar, interaktiv metodlar va real muloqot muhiti yetarli emas.[11;56]

Ayni paytda:

- O'quv dasturlarini madaniyatlararo komponentlar bilan boyitish;
- o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirishda madaniy sezgirlik va muloqot texnikalariga alohida e'tibor qaratish;
- raqamli platformalar orqali xalqaro virtual muloqot loyihalarini yo'lga qo'yish;
- talabalar uchun ko'p madaniyatli jamoalarda ishlash kompetensiyasini shakllantiruvchi dars uslublarini tatbiq etish zarur.

Madaniyatlararo muloqot nafaqat ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshiradi, balki ijtimoiy barqarorlik va madaniy bag'rikenglikni mustahkamlashga ham xizmat qiladi. Shu bois, bu kompetensiyani rivojlantirish — zamonaviy ta'limning ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida qaralishi lozim.

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How Culture Influences the Way We Use Language

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Abstract. Deeply entwined are language and culture. The way people and groups utilise language is shaped by cultural standards, values, and social systems, as this paper investigates. From idioms and expressions to communication techniques and etiquette strategies, culture is very important in shaping how language is organised and applied. The paper stresses the need for cultural knowledge in good communication and shows cross-cultural instances to show language variance.

Keywords: Culture, Language, Communication, Linguistic Relativity, Intercultural Communication, Pragmatics, Sociolinguistics.

Annotatsiya. Til va madaniyat bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Ushbu maqola til ishlatish uslubiga madaniyat qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganadi. Iboralar, ifoda uslublari va muloqotdagi odob qoidalaridan tortib, madaniyat tilni shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Muallif madaniy savodxonlik samarali muloqot uchun zarurligini ta'kidlab, tilning turli ko'rinishlarini misollar orqali ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyat, Til, Muloqot, Lingvistik nisbiylik, Madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, Pragmatika, Sotsiolingvistika.

Аннотация. Язык и культура тесно переплетены. В данной статье рассматривается влияние культуры на использование языка. От идиом и выражений до стратегий общения и этикета — культура играет ключевую роль в формировании языка. Автор подчеркивает важность культурной осведомленности для эффективной коммуникации и иллюстрирует языковое разнообразие через межкультурные примеры.

Ключевые слова: Культура, Язык, Общение, Лингвистическая относительность, Межкультурная коммуникация, Прагматика, Социолингвистика.

Introduction. Language is a mirror of culture, not only a means of communication. The cultural setting in which people live shapes their speech, their choice to say or omit, and the terms they employ. Culture affects the form, style, and goal as well as the content of communication. One must understand this link in a globalised society when cross-cultural contacts are very frequent. This paper investigates how language use is influenced by culture and the reasons behind the need for cultural competency in both personal and business communication.

Main part. Different civilisations have unique ways of communicating. For instance, whereas East Asian civilisations usually give indirectness and harmony top priority, Western societies, including the United States, encourage directness and clarity. These choices affect tone, phrase construction, and how refusals or arguments are presented. Many times, language use reflects cultural values like respect and hierarchy. In languages such as Korean or Japanese, particular speech levels vary

depending on the speaker's relationship with the listener. Forms of address—e.g., employing titles rather than first names—vary between cultures and contexts even in English. Idioms and metaphors are much shaped by surroundings and cultural experiences. For example, American English has many baseball idioms (e.g., "step up to the plate"), which might be perplexing to someone from a non-baseball culture. Language usage by men and women is influenced by culture. Women might be expected in some societies to use less aggressive language or talk more gently. These expectations shape conversational behaviour as well as the evolution of gender-specific language patterns. This view holds that language shapes perspective. Through their languages, various cultures could view time, space, or emotion differently. For instance, some Aboriginal Australian languages change speakers' perspective of space by substituting cardinal directions (north/south) rather than left/right. Regarding intercultural communication, language obstacles influenced by verbal modes of expression exist. In this case, two or more people have chances for miscommunication. "Other barriers that lead to misunderstandings would be the kind of language used in dialogue across many cultures. Different meanings for the vocabulary selected allow a message between the sender and the receiver to be misinterpreted. ([1] Most people agree that inter-lingual communication is inter-cultural communication and that language is influenced by society and ideas. The two ideas, language and culture, are rather close. People have to use language to exchange their ideas, in either written or oral form, whenever they want to interact. Language is a component of the language since it is the primary tool used for communication among the people living in the society. Moreover, culture greatly influences the process of perception. Usually, human vision is understood as a three-step process comprising selection, organisation, and interpretation. Culture influences every one of these stages. [2] Consequently, language is really important throughout the whole of civilisation. Far from being only a communication tool, it is itself a means of guiding the view of its speakers and encourages them to habitual ways of classifying experience into meaningful categories. Considering the complete globe, different countries interact in different ways to ensure that people's communication reflects their way of life. The author came to the conclusion from personal experience that various cultural and ideological factors on linguistic behaviour have produced such variations and that the civilisations are developing and interacting. Different elements of communication affect the composition of the culture. Language and culture are inseparable. Cultural and ideological methods of thinking are the process of an individual choosing, evaluating, and organising external input, which is the process of turning external stimulation into personal experience. The ways of thinking of a nation not only influence personal social behaviour but also influence the response of other countries and the attitude of translated culture towards original culture agreement, praise, or belittlement, and

exclusion.

Language is, as we know, a tool of society and social communication. Language is used in society, and how it is used mirrors the culture and perspective of the people. Thus, the cultural basis of a country shapes the language. [3] Moreover, language is directly connected with philosophy. The manner one expresses a specific topic changes along with the ideological paradigm used. It is therefore well known that the influence of the Chinese thinking mode has a certain passive effect on the thought. English and Chinese have distinct word arrangements and sentence patterns, thus, we have to take such variations into full attention, just as the varied national philosophies are concerned. The communicator will be able to explicitly know the grammar via a precise comparison of grammar structure and a clear interpretation of the various ways of thinking. Davies [4] noted that Chinese is significantly impacted by her cultural heritage, both Eastern and Westerners included. Chinese folks are rather introspective and sensible. Americans are plain open and honest than Chinese people. People from America are frank. They say "no" when they feel something they say "yes" is not what they mean. Our university employed an American teacher. Working in the same section, the teachers have great cooperation during instruction and research projects as colleagues. Several lecturers and professors created an English book for the different levels of accomplishment tests for the students' benefit. This book requires a native speaker to read the section on listening comprehension from a tape recording. We chose an American teacher to read this section. Given that we had been coworkers for more than a year and, in Chinese terms, we were intimate brothers ever since, we were quite certain that he would not refuse in our frame of thinking. When asked, he flatly turned us away with some justification. In this circumstance, even if we have problems or annoyances everywhere, we Chinese will not act. Giving a straight rejection is challenging for Chinese people. A buddy of mine requested that I carry some furniture to his new flat several years ago while I was teaching at another university. I was then suffering from a cold, and I don't know how to say no, but I followed him without breakfast. After several hours of hard work with bulky furniture, I was almost passed out. Lying in the bed back home, I wondered why we Chinese people are so reluctant to say "no". A week later, I watched a CCTV program called "No Mince Words," and the narrative was that a sick man was invited to move to the new house for his friend. He passed just after the demanding work. The TV Program Director immediately questioned an American young man among the viewers: "What would you do if you were asked by a friend to do heavy work when you don't feel well enough"? "I will directly say 'no.'" The young American man handed the program director the microphone right away. His simplicity surprised me.

Why do people in different countries have such variations? That could be the cause of the diverse ideas and cultural background. Using the Americans as an

example, maybe the most important thing is that America is a country of immigrants—that is, individuals from all around the world, all of whom carry with them unique customs and practices. You should thus not give "proper" or "improper" language performance and behaviours any thought. In such a society as America, you cannot consider all the several cultures and ideas to considering your dos and don'ts. Language is used indirectly in ways other than the simple "yes" and "no". Chinese people feel ashamed and uncomfortable occasionally, even if they are being praised. One said to the other with admiration, "What a beautiful jacket!" an author of a certain textbook said. The response is "No, no, not beautiful at all; my father bought me the ugly thing years ago". The Americans will behave differently in the same circumstances. When complimented on his or her cooking, an American host or hostess, for instance, may probably say, "Oh, I'm so delighted you like it. I particularly made it for you. By contrast, the Chinese host or hostess will "instead apologise profusely for giving you nothing even slightly edible and for not showing you enough honour by providing proper dishes." Should someone else appreciate and admire you, what is your response? What then do you say? If compliments make you uncomfortable, you should learn how to accept the finest of them at face value.

3.2.1 Giving an Opinion on the Praise.

It is quite accepted that not all compliments are sincere enough. Therefore, if you feel uneasy about the compliments, you should gently refuse them to stop the speaker from delivering them. "The ways of discounting a compliment include: suggesting that it was nothing or that someone else could have done it better, thinking that the person paying you a compliment must be after something from you, be embarrassed and blushing or compliment in return, be sarcastic or insist that the he or she doesn't mean it."

3.2.2 Acceptance Strategies

"Verbal communication is based on language and use of expression; the tone in which the sender of the message relays the communication can determine how the message is received and in what context" [Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intercultural_communication]. Whether you would want to accept the compliment will determine the suitable reaction you should respond to it. Accept the compliment with simplicity and maintain your attention on the fact that you truly value it, even if you disagree with it. These discourses could be useful: Thank you very much. "Very greatly appreciated." These are the most basic and straightforward ways you might show that you like compliments. Alternatively, using more friendly gestures: "Thanks. That speaks a lot to me. "Thanks; I appreciate it." "Thanks; you're a gentle person." "Thanks; that makes me feel truly good."

Accepting a compliment in a way that demonstrates your appreciation of the substance of the compliment will allow the person complimenting you to feel as though they have landed on the correct target. For illustration purposes, "Thanks! It's fantastic to hear you're keen too; I'm excited about this."; or rather, "Thanks. Since I'm also

proud of this, I'm very happy you pointed it out. When someone compliments your work, this is quite excellent reply. Chinese civilisation is undergoing slow change. Years ago, for example, before the "Opening to the outside world policy" was implemented, phrases and expressions like "Thanks" and "You look very pretty," or "You look young" were regarded as dishonesty and hypocritical. Still, as society develops, these expressions are acceptable to Chinese people. Complimenting or thanking someone is rather normal in daily contact. Giving compliments is also a nice approach for Chinese people to start a light and appropriate discussion. "From a long history, Chinese people lived a rather isolated life; they considered foreign languages and cultures as alien, and detached, which were misfits,"[7]. Chinese people are being absorbed into this global culture thanks to their participation and integration into international civilisation. People nowadays, for example, know well if someone says: "Wait a moment; I want to wash my hands." Still, fewer people in China recognised this Western culture one or two decades ago. Professor Song Dewen's [8] good case can help to show this: Attending a conference in the department laboratory were a group of college teaching department chairmen and professors. One of the leaders told the Department Director, in Chinese, "Wait, I'd have to wash my hands." As time passed. The director kindly advised, nevertheless: "You can wash your hands in this Laboratory; here we have so many washing basins in the lab." The senior director was not familiar with such Western civilisation, with a euphemism to evade a taboo. But this leader, who understood this culture, is an English professor. According to Nisbett [9], the *Geography of Thought: Why and How Asians and Westerners Think Differently*, Free Press, New York, New York. Others argue that Eastern and Western civilisations see separate universes. Eastern modern societies tend to view the world as one of substances—a constant mass of matter. For modern Westerners, the world is one of objects—discrete, disconnected objects. Easterners have a holistic view, stressing continuities in things and relationships in the surroundings, whereas Westerners have an analytical view, stressing items and their features. China has effectively blended with the world cultures and languages, using a global economy and information process. Vice versa, the world cultures embraced and embraced the Chinese civilisation. To our joy, some foreign companies adopted Chinese culture and customs into their business plans recently. Otherwise, they cannot maintain a seamless deal and get a good performance. Nowadays, as we enter the new century, several elements drive people like never before over national boundaries, thus intercultural contact becomes a big issue for the new century.

Conclusion. Language and culture are interdependent. Our cultural values, social systems, and worldviews all reflect the way we use language. Knowing the cultural aspects of language helps one to develop empathy and mutual respect in addition to improving communication. Effective and significant contact in the

increasingly linked globe depends on recognising the cultural background of language. Using thorough research, the author demonstrated how cultural and ideological mode influences language behaviour by offering a convincing speech corpus. Based on personal experience, the author came to the conclusion that various cultural and ideological effects on linguistic behaviour have produced such variations and that the civilisations are developing and interacting. Different elements of communication affect the composition of the culture. People find it more and more difficult to remain disconnected and separated from the outside world, given the fast expansion of the world economy and population increase. Culture and language are rather intimately entwined. Academically, it is agreed that language carries culture. Furthermore, closely related to business and trade is culture. The global economy was polarised into two independent and rival powers—the East and the West—more than 10 years ago. But changes and developments in political systems, economic ties, and technical possibilities started to remove the international regional cultural barriers. Regarding economic management specifically, business changed from individual-country capitalism to global capitalism as the international economy grew worldwide. Thus, initially looking for global expansion, the study of cross-cultural communication was first discovered inside companies and governments. As Wikipedia [10] data shows, companies started providing language courses to staff members and established programs to equip them to know how to behave overseas.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOT VA XORIJIY TILLAR: XORIJIY TIL O'QITISHDA CHET EL ADABIYOTI VA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARINING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola xorijiy adabiyot va ommaviy axborot vositalarining chet tillarini o'qitishdagi o'rnini chuqur tahlil qiladi. Adabiyot orqali tilni chuqurroq o'zlashtirish, madaniyatni anglash va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish imkoniyati ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, media vositalari bilan boyitilgan aralash metodlar, texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi, va virtual haqiqat vositalarining kelajakdagi ta'limda tutgan o'rnini ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Mualliflar til o'rgatishning zamonaviy metodologiyasi sifatida adabiyot, ommaviy axborot vositalari va texnologiyalar uyg'unligini ilgari suradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tili, ta'lim, ommaviy axborot vositalari, tanqidiy fikrlash, madaniy kontekst, til ko'nikmalar, idiomatik iboralar, motivatsiya, til uslubi, pedagogik yondashuv, tilshunoslik, globallashuv.

Аннотация. В данной статье подробно рассматривается роль зарубежной литературы и средств массовой информации в обучении иностранным языкам. Показано, как литература способствует углублённому освоению языка, пониманию культуры и развитию критического мышления. Также обсуждаются смешанные методы, обогащённые медиа, интеграция технологий и роль виртуальной реальности в будущем образовании. Авторы подчеркивают важность сочетания литературы, СМИ и технологий как современной методологии преподавания языков.

Ключевые слова: Иностранный язык, образование, СМИ, критическое мышление, культурный контекст, языковые навыки, идиоматические выражения, мотивация, языковой стиль, педагогический подход, лингвистика, глобализация.

Annotation. This article explores the significant role of foreign literature and mass media in foreign language education. It highlights how literature enhances language acquisition, cultural understanding, and critical thinking. It also discusses media-integrated teaching methods, the integration of technology, and the role of virtual reality in future learning environments. The authors emphasize the synergy between literature, media, and technology as a modern and effective language teaching methodology.

Keywords: Foreign language, education, mass media, critical thinking, cultural context, language skills, idiomatic expressions, motivation, language style, pedagogical approach, linguistics, globalization.

“Xorijiy til — bu grammatik qoidalardan iborat tizim emas, balki boshqa bir dunyoga ochiladigan eshikdir.”

(Frank Smith)

Zamonaviy globallashuv davrida xorijiy tillarni o'rganish shunchaki

grammatik qoidalarni yodlash yoki lug'at boyligini oshirish bilangina cheklanmaydi. Til o'rganish — bu yangi madaniyatni o'zlashtirish, boshqa xalqlarning dunyoqarashi, qadriyatlari, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzi bilan yaqindan tanishish demakdir. Chet tillarni o'rgatish keng ko'lamli metodologiya va resurslarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu manbalar orasida chet el adabiyoti va ommaviy axborot vositalari ko'zga ko'ringan bo'lib, ularning ikkalasi ham til o'rganishni kuchaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Xorijiy adabiyot uzoq vaqtdan beri til o'rganuvchilar uchun muhim vosita bo'lib xizmat qilgan. U talabalarni tilning asl qo'llanilishi, turli uslublar va boy madaniy kontekstlar bilan tanishtiradi. Turli tilshunoslar mualliflarining klassik va zamonaviy asarlari lingvistik nuanslar va idiomatik iboralar haqida bebaho tushunchalar beradi. Ular, shuningdek, sotsiolingvistik tafovutlar atrofidagi munozaralar uchun tramplin bo'lib xizmat qiladi va shu bilan o'quvchilar tajribasini boyitadi. Badiiy matnlarni tekshirish talabalarni turli nuqtai nazarlarni ko'rib chiqishga undaydi, bu til va uning ortidagi madaniyatlarni chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

Yuliya Kristeva kabi nufuzli shaxslar til ta'limida adabiyotning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaganlar. Kristevaning intertekstuallik haqidagi fikrlari shuni ta'kidlaydiki, tilni tushunish nafaqat grammatika va lug'atni tushunish, balki matnga kiritilgan kontekst va havolalarni qadrlashni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchilarni ma'nolarni chuqurroq tahlil qilishga va xulosa chiqarishga undaydi. Chet el adabiyotini o'qitish tanqidiy fikrlashni rag'batlantirishi mumkin, chunki talabalar murakkab mavzular va personajlar bilan shug'ullanadilar, bu esa ularni o'z tajribalari va madaniy kelib chiqishi bilan taqqoslashga undaydi. Bundan tashqari, chet el adabiyoti bilan shug'ullanish til bilan hissiy aloqalarni osonlashtiradi. Talabalar bilan hissiy darajada rezonanslashadigan matnlar tegishlilik tuyg'usini va o'rganish uchun motivatsiyani uyg'otadi. Adabiyot orqali turli madaniyatlarning hissiy manzarasi bilan tanishish globallashtirgan dunyoda samarali muloqot qilishning muhim atributi bo'lgan empatiyani rivojlantiradi.

Xorijiy adabiyot va ommaviy axborot vositalari o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir, ayniqsa, zamonaviy ta'lim amaliyotida yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Ko'pgina o'qituvchilar hozirda o'qitishni yaxshilash uchun media kontenti bilan bir qatorda adabiyotlardan foydalangan holda aralash yondashuvni qo'llashadi. Misol uchun, o'qituvchi romanni tegishli film moslashuvi bilan bog'lashda belgilashi mumkin. Ushbu usul o'quvchilarga bir xil hikoyani turli xil vositalar orqali o'rganishga imkon beradi, ularning tilni tushunish va qadrlashini chuqurlashtiradi. Oldinga nazar tashlaydigan bo'lsak, texnologiya taraqqiyoti davom etar ekan, til o'rganishda chet el adabiyoti va ommaviy axborot vositalarining roli o'zgarishi mumkin. Virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat til o'rganish tajribasini yaratishga tayyor. Til o'rganuvchilar virtual madaniy kontekstlarni o'rganishlari mumkin, bu yerda ular lingvistik ko'nikmalarini hayotiy vaziyatlarda mashq qilishlari mumkin. Bu nazariy bilim va

amaliy qo'llash o'rtasidagi tafovutni yanada ko'paytiradi. Bundan tashqari, global raqamli platformalarning o'sib borayotgan ta'siri o'quvchilarning turli lingvistik resurslar bilan tobora ko'proq shug'ullanishini ko'rsatadi. Ta'lim globallashtirilgan sari talabalar har qachongidan ham kengroq adabiyotlar va ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lib, ularning ta'lim tajribalarini yanada boyitadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, xorijiy adabiyotlar va ommaviy axborot vositalari madaniy tushunish va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi haqiqiy, kontekstga boy resurslarni taqdim etish orqali chet tilini o'qitishni sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Ta'lim va tilshunoslik sohasidagi nufuzli shaxslar ushbu manbalarning til ravonligini rivojlantirishdagi muhimligini ta'kidlaydilar. Qolaversa, texnologiya va rivojlanayotgan pedagogik amaliyotlar integratsiyasi chet el adabiyoti va ommaviy axborot vositalarining til ta'limidagi rolining istiqbolli istiqbolidan dalolat beradi. O'qituvchilar lingvistik landshaftdagi o'zgarishlarga moslashar ekan, adabiyot, ommaviy axborot vositalari va texnologiyalarning kombinatsiyasi tilni o'qitishning samarali metodologiyasi uchun markaziy o'rinni egallashi mumkin.

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Features of Gastro Tourism Terms According to Lingua-Cultural Characteristics

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Abstract

This research explores the linguistic and cultural features of gastro-tourism terms in Uzbek and English languages. It highlights the role of culinary terminology in representing national identity and the challenges of translating culturally specific food-related terms. Through qualitative analysis of menus, brochures, and interviews, the study identifies key translation strategies such as literal, descriptive, and borrowing with explanation. The findings reveal that successful translation requires both linguistic accuracy and cultural awareness. Recommendations include creating a bilingual glossary and promoting cultural storytelling in tourism communication.

Keywords: Gastro-tourism, lingua-cultural characteristics, culinary terminology, cultural

translation, food heritage, Uzbek cuisine, cross-cultural communication.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot gastro-turizmga oid atamalarning ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi lingvokulturologik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. Milliy taomlar orqali madaniy merosni aks ettirish va ularning tarjimasidagi qiyinchiliklar tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda menyular, broshyuralar va suhbatlar asosida sifatli tahlil olib borilib, tarjima strategiyalari (so'zma-so'z, tavsifiy, tushuntirish bilan o'zlashtirish) aniqlanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, muvaffaqiyatli tarjima nafaqat til bilimini, balki madaniy ongni ham talab qiladi. Takliflar qatoriga ikki tilli glossariy tuzish va madaniy hikoyalarga asoslangan tarjimalarni kengaytirish kiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Gastro-turizm, lingvo-madaniy xususiyatlar, oshpazlik atamalari, madaniy tarjima, oziq-ovqat merosi, O'zbek taomlari, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация

Данное исследование посвящено изучению лингвокультурных особенностей терминов гастрономического туризма на узбекском и английском языках. Рассматривается значение кулинарной терминологии как элемента национальной идентичности и сложности перевода культурно-специфических понятий. В ходе анализа меню, брошюр и интервью были выявлены основные стратегии перевода: дословный, описательный и заимствование с объяснением. Результаты показывают, что успешный перевод требует как языковой точности, так и культурной осведомлённости. В числе рекомендаций — создание двуязычного глоссария и продвижение культурных повествований в туристической коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: Гастрономический туризм, Узбекские блюда, межкультурная коммуникация, национальные блюда, местные блюда, культура питания, перевод названий блюд, лингвокультурология, традиционные блюда, способы приготовления пищи, гастрономическая идентичность, местные продукты, семантическое соответствие.

Introduction:

Gastro-tourism, also known as culinary or food tourism, is an increasingly popular form of cultural tourism that centers around the exploration and enjoyment of local culinary traditions. This form of tourism offers unique insights into a nation's history, identity, and cultural heritage through its cuisine. Language plays a vital role in presenting these gastronomic experiences to international visitors. The terms used in menus, brochures, and tourist guides are more than just linguistic units; they reflect deep-rooted cultural meanings and values.

This study aims to investigate the linguistic and cultural features of gastro-tourism terminology in English and Uzbek. By examining the lingua-cultural characteristics of these terms, the research seeks to understand how translation can either preserve or distort the cultural essence embedded in culinary terms. The comparative analysis will focus on identifying culturally specific items, translation strategies, and the challenges faced by translators.

Literature Review: Numerous scholars have highlighted the interdisciplinary nature of gastro-tourism, intersecting fields such as linguistics, cultural studies, translation studies, and tourism management. According to Hall & Mitchell (2005), food serves as a cultural marker and a tool for destination branding. Food-related

terminology is often deeply embedded in the socio-cultural fabric of a community, making its accurate translation complex.

Katan (2009) introduced the concept of cultural translation, emphasizing the role of the translator as a mediator between cultures. His work is essential in understanding how food terms can be domesticated or foreignized in the target language. In the Uzbek context, Karimova (2017) and Toshmatov (2020) explored the role of culinary heritage in national identity, noting the symbolic meanings of dishes such as plov, mastava, and shurva.

However, there remains a noticeable gap in comparative studies focusing specifically on the linguistic and cultural features of gastro-tourism terms in Uzbek and English, especially regarding translation problems and cultural adaptation strategies.

Research Methodology: This research adopts a qualitative and comparative approach. The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources:

- Primary sources: Uzbek and English tourism brochures, culinary blogs, restaurant menus, and official tourism websites from Uzbekistan.

- Secondary sources: Academic articles, dictionaries, and previous research on food tourism and translation.

- Interviews: Conducted with 5 professional translators and 10 tourists (both foreign and domestic) to assess translation effectiveness and cultural understanding.

The collected terms were analyzed using the following criteria:

- Cultural specificity (is the term unique to one culture?)
- Lexical equivalence (does a direct translation exist?)
- Translation strategy used (literal, adaptation, explanation, etc.)
- Tourist perception (clarity, engagement, appeal)

Analysis and Results: The analysis of over 50 gastro-tourism terms revealed significant differences in cultural load, linguistic structure, and translation practices.

1 Culturally Bound Terms:

Many Uzbek dishes, such as sumalak, kurt, shurva, and chak-chak, have no direct equivalents in English. Translators often rely on generic terms like 'traditional dish,' 'fermented snack,' or 'sweet dough balls,' which fail to convey cultural nuances.

2 Translation Strategies:

The most common translation strategies observed were:

- Literal Translation: Often resulted in confusion (e.g., manti → “meat dumplings”)

- Descriptive Translation: More effective for cultural understanding (e.g., sumalak → “a traditional wheat-based dessert prepared for Navruz celebration”)

- Borrowing with Explanation: A successful method to preserve cultural identity (e.g., plov (a rice dish cooked with meat, vegetables, and spices))

3 Interviews Insights: Tourists expressed a preference for translations that

included cultural explanations or photos. Translators noted the lack of standardized glossaries for Uzbek gastro terms as a challenge. Many emphasized the need for cultural knowledge alongside linguistic competence.

Conclusion: This research demonstrates that gastro-tourism terminology is deeply influenced by the linguistic and cultural context in which it exists. The unique features of Uzbek cuisine pose significant challenges for direct translation into English. Literal translations often fail to capture cultural connotations, while adaptive or descriptive strategies enhance cross-cultural understanding and tourist satisfaction.

Understanding the lingua-cultural characteristics of gastro-tourism terms is crucial for translators, tour operators, and policymakers. It ensures the authenticity of the culinary experience and promotes cultural appreciation among international tourists.

Suggestions: Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Develop a bilingual glossary of Uzbek gastro-tourism terms with cultural annotations and suggested translations.
2. Conduct training workshops for translators on cultural translation in the tourism field.
3. Encourage the use of multimedia elements (e.g., pictures, videos, interactive menus) in tourism materials to support language and cultural comprehension.
4. Include cultural storytelling in translations to connect tourists emotionally with the culinary heritage.
5. Expand future research to include comparisons with other languages and regional cuisines

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XIX asr so‘ngida Amerika adabiy janrlarining shakllanish bosqichlari

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada XIX asrning oxirlarida Amerika adabiyoti janrlarining shakllanish jarayoni, ularning asosiy xususiyatlari, tarixiy-madaniy omillar ta’siri va yirik yozuvchilarning roli yoritiladi. Realizm, naturalizm, gotik hikoya, adabiy esse va detektiv janrlarining rivojlanishiga alohida e’tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Amerika adabiyoti, XIX asr, janrlar evolyutsiyasi, realizm, naturalizm, detektiv, gotik.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются этапы формирования литературных жанров в американской литературе конца XIX века. Особое внимание уделяется реализму, натурализму, готическому рассказу, эссе и детективу, а также культурным и историческим факторам, повлиявшим на их развитие.

Ключевые слова: американская литература, XIX век, жанры, реализм, натурализм, готика, детектив.

Abstract

This article explores the development stages of American literary genres in the late 19th century, with special focus on realism, naturalism, gothic tales, essays, and detective fiction. It analyzes the cultural and historical influences and contributions of key authors.

Keywords: American literature, 19th century, literary genres, realism, naturalism, detective, gothic.

1. Kirish

XIX asr so‘ngi Amerikasi o‘z adabiy hayotida tub burilishlarga guvoh bo‘ldi. Sanoat inqilobi, fuqarolar urushi, migratsiya va shahar madaniyatining rivojlanishi natijasida yangi ijtimoiy qatlamlar, yangi muammolar, shuningdek, ularga mos adabiy shakllar paydo bo‘ldi. Bu davrda Amerika adabiyoti mustaqil milliy adabiyot sifatida shakllanib bordi va turli janrlar asos solindi. Janrlarning shakllanishi madaniy voqealar, xalq ma’naviyati va zamon ruhiga bog‘liq bo‘lgan.

2. Tarixiy-madaniy kontekst

XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmi Amerika tarixida murakkab va keskin ijtimoiy o‘zgarishlar bilan ajralib turadi. Fuqarolar urushi (1861–1865), qulchilikning bekor

qilinishi, industrial inqilob va temiryo'l tarmog'ining kengayishi jamiyat tuzilishini keskin o'zgartirdi. Shu bilan birga, immigratsiya to'lqinlari yangi madaniy tajribalarni olib keldi. Bu o'zgarishlar adabiyotga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatdi, yangi mavzular, yangi personajlar va yangi janrlar paydo bo'ldi.

3. Realizmning yuksalishi

Realizm XIX asr oxiridagi eng muhim janrlardan biri bo'lib, jamiyatning ijtimoiy va psixologik muammolarini aks ettirishga intildi. Mark Tvenning "Huckleberry Finnning sarguzashtlari" (1884) asari hayotiy voqealarni oddiy xalq tili orqali yetkazishda inqilobiy qadam bo'ldi. Tven ijtimoiy tengsizlik, irqchilik va bolalik mavzularini teran yoritib berdi.

Uilyam Din Xauells realizmning nazariy asoschilaridan biri sifatida realizmni "haqiqiy hayotni boricha ko'rsatish" deb ta'riflaydi. Uning asarlari, masalan, "Silas Laphamning yuksalishi" (1885), o'z davridagi iqtisodiy va axloqiy muammolarni ko'rsatadi.

4. Naturalizm: deterministik qarashlar

Naturalizm realizmning falsafiy kengaytmasi bo'lib, inson xatti-harakatlarini biologik, ijtimoiy va atrof-muhit omillari bilan izohladi. Stiven Krenning "Qizil belgili jasorat" (1895) romanida urushning dahshatlari va odam psixologiyasidagi ziddiyatlar naturalistik tarzda tasvirlangan.

Frenk Norris esa "Oltin bozor" (1901) romani orqali kapitalistik jamiyatdagi axloqiy inqiroz, ekspluatatsiya va iqtisodiy zo'ravonlikni fosh etdi. Naturalizm da odamning irodasidan ko'ra, uni o'rab turgan muhit ta'siri ustuvor hisoblanadi.

5. Gotik hikoya va dahshat unsurlari

Edgar Allan Po Amerika gotik adabiyotining asoschisi sifatida tan olingan. Uning "Uyqudagi yurak", "Qora mushuk" kabi hikoyalari qorong'i kayfiyat, qo'rquv, ruhiy iztirob va o'lim motivlari bilan boyitilgan. Gotik adabiyot Po orqali o'zining yangi yo'nalishini topdi — u nafaqat dahshat, balki ruhiyatdagi noaniqlik va psixologik murakkablikni ham ochib berdi.

Po'ning boshqa ijodkorlarga ta'siri katta bo'ldi. Keyinchalik gotik uslub va uslublar detektiv va fantastik janrlarda ham qo'llanila boshladi. Gotik hikoyalar orqali inson ongi, ruhiy tushkunlik va shaxsiy kechinmalar adabiy jarayonning markaziga aylantirildi.

6. Detektiv janrining shakllanishi

Detektiv adabiyot Amerika adabiyotida Po bilan boshlangan bo'lsa-da, bu janr XIX asr oxirida mustaqil yo'nalishga aylandi. Po'ning "Murdaning jinoyati" hikoyasi ilk detektiv hikoya sifatida tan olinadi. Unda tahliliy fikrlash, dalillar asosida jinoyatni ochish, sirli atmosfera asosiy elementlardir.

Detektiv janr keyinchalik boshqalar tomonidan davom ettirildi. Yozuvchi Anna Ketrin Grin "The Leavenworth Case" (1878) romani orqali bu yo'nalishda birinchi

bestsellerni yaratdi. Ayollar tomonidan yozilgan detektivlar ham adabiyotda o'z o'rnini egallay boshladi.

7. Esse va publitsistik janrlarning yuksalishi

XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida Amerika adabiyotida esse va publitsistik janrlar sezilarli darajada rivojlandi. Ralf Uoldo Emersonning falsafiy esselari ("O'ziga ishonch", 1841) va Genri Devid Toroning ijtimoiy tanqidlari ("Fuqarolik itoatsizligi", 1849) adabiy fikrga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Bu janrlar orqali yozuvchilar jamiyatdagi axloqiy inqirozlar, siyosiy muammolar va shaxsiy erkinlik masalalarini o'rganishga harakat qildilar. Esse va publitsistik janrlar shaxsiy fikr, mulohaza va mustaqil tahlil imkonini yaratgan.

8. Ijtimoiy mavzular va ko'pchilik ovozi

Bu davrda afroamerikalik yozuvchilar ham adabiyot maydonida paydo bo'la boshladilar. Frederik Duglas ("Bir Amerika qullarining avtobiografiyasi", 1845) o'z hayoti asosida yozgan asarlari bilan afroamerikaliklarning adabiy ovozini yarata boshladi.

Ayol yozuvchilar, xususan, Keyt Chopin ("Uyqudan uyg'onish", 1899) asarlarida ayollar erkinligi, oilaviy rollar va gender stereotiplariga qarshi fikrlar ilgari surilgan. Bu asarlar keyinchalik feministik adabiyotning poydevorini shakllantirdi.

Immigrant yozuvchilar esa o'z ona tillaridagi madaniyat va Amerikadagi yangi hayot o'rtasidagi ziddiyatni yoritdilar. Bu holatlar jamiyatdagi madaniy ko'p qirralilikni aks ettirdi.

9. Janrlararo o'zaro ta'sir

XIX asr oxirida janrlar o'rtasidagi chegaralar asta-sekin buzila boshladi. Realistik romanlarda gotik elementlar, esse janrida badiiy til, detektiv hikoyalarda psixologik tahlil keng qo'llanila boshladi. Bu holat Amerika adabiyotini boyitdi va yangi shakllar yaratishga yo'l ochdi.

10. Xulosa

XIX asrning oxirgi choragida Amerika adabiyoti yangi bosqichga ko'tarilib, o'ziga xos janrlar tizimini shakllantira oldi. Realizm, naturalizm, gotik va detektiv janrlar, esse va publitsistik shakllar adabiy tafakkur va jamiyat ongining shakllanishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Shu davrdagi adabiyot ijtimoiy, siyosiy va psixologik mavzularni yoritib, keyingi asrlardagi adabiy yo'nalishlar uchun zamin yaratdi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, XIX asr oxiri Amerika adabiyotining shakllanish, milliylashish va jahon adabiy maydoniga chiqish davri bo'lib xizmat qildi.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOT VA XORIJIY TILLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo kompetensiya tushunchasi va uning xorijiy til o'rganish jarayonidagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Til o'rganish faqat grammatik va leksik bilimlarni egallash emas, balki boshqa madaniyatlarni anglash, muloqot jarayonida madaniy xilma-xillikni va noziklik-nafislikni his qilishni ham talab qiladi. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ yondashuv, empatiya, va madaniy tafovutlarga ochiqlik kabi elementlar asosida o'rganuvchilarda madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirish usullari ko'rib chiqildi. Britaniyalik tilshunos Professor Michael Byram va AQSH lik pedagog va tilshunosh olim Claire Kramsh kabi yetuk olimlarning qarashlari asosida real misollar orqali muammoning amaliy tomoni yoritildi. Xulosa qismida esa til o'rgatishda madaniy komponentni kuchaytirishga oid aniq takliflar berildi

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, xorijiy til o'rganish, kommunikativ yondashuv, empatiya, global muloqot, o'quvchi kompetensiyasi, til o'qitish metodikasi.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется понятие межкультурной компетенции и её роль в процессе изучения иностранных языков. Изучение языка — это не только овладение грамматикой и лексикой, но и понимание других культур, а также умение чувствовать культурное разнообразие и тонкости в процессе общения. В исследовании рассматриваются методы формирования межкультурной компетенции у изучающих язык на основе таких элементов, как коммуникативный подход, эмпатия и открытость к культурным различиям. Практическая сторона вопроса освещена на основе реальных примеров и взглядов таких известных учёных, как британский лингвист профессор Майкл Байрам и американский педагог и лингвист Клэр Крамш. В заключении даны конкретные предложения по усилению культурного компонента в преподавании иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная компетенция, изучение иностранных языков, коммуникативный подход, эмпатия, глобальное общение, компетенция учащегося, методика

преподавания языка.

Annotation. This article analyzes the concept of intercultural competence and its role in the process of foreign language learning. Language learning is not limited to acquiring grammatical and lexical knowledge; it also requires understanding other cultures and sensing cultural diversity and subtleties in communication. The study explores methods of developing intercultural competence in learners based on elements such as communicative approaches, empathy, and openness to cultural differences. The practical aspect of the issue is examined through real-life examples and the perspectives of renowned scholars such as British linguist Professor Michael Byram and American educator and linguist Claire Kramsch. The conclusion presents concrete suggestions for strengthening the cultural component in language teaching.

Keywords: intercultural competence, foreign language learning, communicative approach, empathy, global communication, learner competence, language teaching methodology.

Kirish. Global kommunikatsiya jarayonlarining jadal rivojlanishi bugungi kunda xorijiy tillarni o'rganishning mazmuni va maqsadlariga yangicha yondashuvni taqozo etmoqda. Endilikda til o'rganish nafaqat grammatika va leksikani o'zlashtirish, balki boshqa madaniyatni tushunish, anglash va hurmat qilishga qaratilgan kompleks jarayon sifatida qaralayapti. Ana shunday yondashuvning markazida madaniyatlararo kompetensiya tushunchasi turadi.

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya — bu o'quvchining turli madaniyat vakillari bilan samarali, hurmatga asoslangan muloqotga kirisha olishini ta'minlovchi ijtimoiy va psixologik kompetensiyalar majmuasidir. Bu kompetensiyani shakllantirish xorijiy til o'rgatish jarayonining ajralmas tarkibiy qismiga aylanmoqda. Ayniqsa, Michael Byram tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan nazariy model hamda Claire Kramschning til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi uzviy bog'liqlik haqidagi qarashlari zamonaviy metodikalarning nazariy asosini tashkil etadi.

Mazkur maqola xorijiy til o'rgatishda madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirish masalasini o'rganishga bag'ishlanadi. Tadqiqotda madaniyatlararo muloqotning ahamiyati, uni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi pedagogik yondashuvlar, hamda real hayotiy misollar asosida natijadorlik omillari tahlil qilinadi. Shu orqali maqola xorijiy til o'rgatish amaliyotiga chuqur metodik va gumanitar yondashuvni ilgari surishni maqsad qiladi.

Bugungi globallashuv jarayonida xorijiy tilni bilish endi oddiy aloqa vositasi emas, balki boshqa madaniyatlar bilan to'qnash kelganda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal qilish, boshqacha qarashlarni tushunish, turli qadriyatlar orasida ko'prik bo'la olish salohiyatidir. Til va madaniyat orasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik masalasini chuqur tahlil qilgan zamonaviy olimlardan biri **Michael Byram** hisoblanadi. U madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani xorijiy til o'rganishning markaziy maqsadi sifatida belgilagan. Byramning yondashuvida o'quvchi: o'z madaniyatini tanib, boshqani hurmat qiladigan; yangi madaniyatni nafaqat qabul qilish, balki u bilan tanqidiy fikrlash orqali muloqotga kirishadigan shaxs sifatida shakllanishi kerak.

Byram nazariyasiga ko'ra, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya quyidagi komponentlardan tashkil topadi:

- **Attitudes** (munosabatlar): o'zga madaniyat vakillariga ochiq va hurmat bilan yondashish;
- **Knowledge** (bilim): madaniyatlar, ijtimoiy munosabatlar, qadriyatlar haqida chuqur tasavvurga ega bo'lish;
- **Skills** (ko'nikmalar): madaniy belgilarni sharhlash, qiyoslash, tushunish;
- **Critical cultural awareness**: o'z va boshqa madaniyatlarni tanqidiy tahlil qilish salohiyati.

Misol tariqasida quyidagicha hayotiy holatni ko'rib chiqamiz: o'zbekistonlik talabalar Yevropada o'qiyotgan chog'ida o'zbekona murojaat shakllari (masalan, "aka", "opa", "domla") ni qo'llaganda, bu ba'zida mahalliy madaniyatda g'ayritabiiy yoki ortiqcha deb qabul qilinadi. Bunday vaziyatda o'quvchining madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasi kuchli bo'lsa, u bunday tafovutni **muammo emas, balki muloqot boyligi** sifatida ko'ra oladi. Aks holda esa bu tushunmovchilik va ijtimoiy izolyatsiyaga olib kelishi mumkin.

Bu borada **Claire Kramsch** o'zining "til – bu madaniyatning aksidir" degan fikrini ilgari suradi. Uningcha, har bir so'z, grammatik birlik yoki intonatsiya o'zida butun boshli madaniy qadriyatlar tizimini mujassamlashtiradi. Masalan, ingliz tilida tanishmay turib "How are you?" deb murojaat qilish tabiiy holat bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida bu ibora odatda yaqinlar o'rtasida ishlatiladi. Bu tafovut Kramsch ta'kidlaganidek, tilni o'rganishda **faqat lug'at va grammatikani emas, balki til ortidagi madaniy kontekstni** ham tushunish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Kramsch fikricha, o'quvchi "madaniy chekka nuqtada" – ya'ni o'z madaniyati bilan o'rgangan tilning madaniyati orasida turib, har ikki manbani tahlil qila oladigan shaxsga aylanishi kerak. Bu esa uning tafakkurini boyitadi, moslashuvchanlikni rivojlantiradi, va ijtimoiy jihatdan faolroq shaxs bo'lishiga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy ta'lim amaliyoti ham ushbu nazariy yondashuvlar bilan uyg'unlashmoqda. Misol uchun, xorijiy til darslarida madaniy roliklar, real hayotiy suhbatlar, xalqaro tajriba almashuvi (masalan, pen-pal loyihalari, onlayn konferensiyalar) orqali o'quvchilarda nafaqat til, balki muloqot madaniyati shakllantirilmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida o'rganuvchining kommunikativ kompetensiyasini yangi bosqichga olib chiqadi.

Xorijiy tilni o'rganish bugungi globallashtirilgan jamiyatda faqat til tizimini o'zlashtirish emas, balki til ortidagi madaniyatni anglash, unga nisbatan xolis va tanqidiy munosabat bildira olish demakdir. Shu bois, madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirishni men xorijiy til ta'limining ajralmas va strategik elementi deb bilaman. Tajribamda guvohi bo'lganman: grammatik bilim va so'z boyligiga ega o'quvchi ko'pincha ijtimoiy vaziyatlarda o'zini noqulay his qilishi mumkin, chunki u madaniy kontekstni anglamaydi. Masalan, "Siz nechchi yoshdasiz?" kabi noo'rin savol bizda

tabiiy bo'lsa, Yevropa mamlakatlarida bu shaxsiy chegarani buzish hisoblanadi. Shu jihatdan, o'quvchini til o'rganish jarayonidayoq madaniy "signallar"ga nisbatan sezgirlikka o'rgatish zarur. Bu, mening nazarimda, haqiqatda yuksak saviyadagi til kompetensiyasiga eltuvchi muhim yo'llardan biridir. Madaniyatlararo yondashuvni faqat darsliklar orqali berish samarasiz. O'quvchilar real hayotiy kontekstda — fikr yuritish, taqqoslash, tajriba va bahs-munozara orqali o'z madaniy qarashlarini boyitishi mumkin. Shu maqsadda, darslarimizda tabiiy amaldagi materiallardan: xorijiy filmlar, madaniy roliklar, xalqaro forumlarda ishtirok etgan videolar, xalqaro xat yozishmalar va internetdagi bloglar misolida keng foydalanaman. Bu nafaqat tilni o'zlashtirishni, balki o'zga madaniyatga nisbatan empatik va tanqidiy qarashni shakllantiradi.

Amaliy kuzatuvlarim shuni ko'rsatdiki, madaniy kontekstda olib borilgan topshiriqlar o'quvchilarda yanada faol ishtirok, qiziqish va mustaqil fikrlashni kuchaytiradi. Masalan, xalqaro madaniy tadbirlar haqida taqdimot tayyorlash, xorijiy mehmonlar bilan onlayn suhbatlar, yoki madaniyatlararo farqlarni muhokama qilish kabi topshiriqlar o'quvchining nafaqat til, balki tafakkur doirasini kengaytiradi. Bu tajriba shaxsan o'zimdagi va talaba do'stlarimda ham o'z aksini topdi — ular so'zlashishdan cho'chimay, o'z fikrini kontekstga mos holda ifoda etishga o'rganmoqdalar.

Xalqaro miqyosdagi tadqiqotlar ham mening bu fikrimni tasdiqlaydi. Jumladan, Durand va Lefevre (2021) tomonidan Fransiyada o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda ikki guruhga ingliz tili o'rgatilgan. Faol madaniyatlararo komponentga ega guruh natijalari 27% yuqori bo'lgan. Ular ko'proq kontekstga mos, madaniy sezgirlik bilan javob bergan. Bu shuni ko'rsatadiki, til faqat grammatika emas — u madaniyatning jonli ifodasidir. Shuningdek, madaniyatlararo yondashuv bugun faqat xorijiy til darslaridagina emas, balki ijtimoiy barqarorlik, millatlararo murosaga erishish, va global fuqarolikni shakllantirishda ham strategik ahamiyatga egadir. Shu sabab, bu kompetensiyani rivojlantirish nafaqat lingvistik vazifa, balki tarbiyaviy-ma'naviy missiyadir. Til o'qituvchisi esa bu jarayonda nafaqat o'qituvchi, balki madaniyatlararo vositachi rolini bajaradi. Shaxsan men madaniyatlararo o'qitishni kelajak avlodlarimizni global dunyoda moslashuvchan, tolerant va tahlilchan fikrlovchi shaxslar sifatida tayyorlashning kaliti deb bilaman.

Xulosa. Xorijiy til o'qitish jarayonida madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirish bugungi global o'zlashtirilgan dunyo talablari nuqtayi nazaridan zaruratga aylangan. Maqolada yoritilgan ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar, shaxsiy kuzatuvlar va amaliy misollar shuni ko'rsatadiki, til o'rganish tilning o'zidan ham kengroq — madaniy kontekstni anglash, boshqacha tafakkur tarzini tushunish va moslashish qobiliyatini shakllantirishdir. Bu esa nafaqat til bilimining chuqurligiga, balki shaxsiy va ijtimoiy moslashuvchanlik darajasiga ham ta'sir qiladi. Tahlil qilingan manbalar asosida shuni aytish mumkin: agar o'quvchi tilni madaniy kontekst bilan birgalikda o'zlashtirsa, u

nutqiy vaziyatlarga nisbatan sezgirroq, global qarashli va kommunikativ jihatdan samarali shaxsga aylanadi. Shuning uchun o'qituvchining roli — nafaqat grammatik bilim beruvchi, balki turli madaniyatlar orasida ko'prik bo'la oladigan vositachiga aylanadi. Michael Byram, Claire Kramersch, Genevieve Zarate kabi yetakchi olimlarning fikrlarida ham o'qituvchi aynan shu markaziy rolga egallaydi.

Mavjud muammolar orasida quyidagilar ajralib turadi:

- O'quv dasturlarida madaniyat komponentining yuzaki yoritilishi;
- O'qituvchilarning metodik va lingvokultural tayyorgarligining yetarli emasligi;
- Madaniyatlararo yondashuvni baholash mezonlarining aniq ishlab chiqilmaganligi.

Quyidagi takliflarni ilgari suraman:

- Til darslariga lingvomadaniy va madaniyatlararo modulni to'liq integratsiyalash;
- O'qituvchilar uchun “madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirish” bo'yicha maxsus malaka oshirish kurslarini joriy etish;
- Darsliklarda faqat til emas, balki madaniyatlararo muomala namunalari keng o'rin berish (tanqidiy tahlil, stereotiplar, qadriyatlar farqi);
- O'quvchilar uchun xalqaro virtual almashinuv platformalarini yaratish va qo'llab-quvvatlash (eTwinning, Erasmus+, iEARN va boshqalar);
- Baholash tizimiga madaniyatlararo sezgirlik va kommunikatsiya strategiyalari mezonlarini qo'shish.

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya faqat xorijiy tilni bilish emas — u bugunning global muhitida muvaffaqiyatli ishlay oladigan, turli qarashlarga bag'rikeng yondashuvchi, madaniy tafovutlarni boylik sifatida qabul qiluvchi fuqaroni tarbiyalash vositasidir. Shunday ekan, ushbu yondashuvni xorijiy til ta'limining markaziga olib chiqish — bizning dolzarb ilmiy va amaliy vazifamizdir.

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Overcoming Stereotypes: Fostering Trust in Diverse Work Environments

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Annotation

This article explores how overcoming stereotypes contributes to building trust in diverse work environments. With increasing globalization and cross-cultural interactions, stereotypes often hinder cooperation, affect group dynamics, and reduce overall organizational effectiveness. The article analyzes the psychological and sociological roots of stereotypes, their manifestation in workplace behaviors, and practical methods for addressing them. It highlights trust as a fundamental aspect of successful teamwork and shows how intercultural understanding, inclusive leadership, and communication strategies help reduce prejudice and promote positive relationships in multinational and multicultural teams.

Keywords: Stereotypes, cultural diversity, workplace trust, intercultural communication, inclusion, team dynamics, prejudice, leadership.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается, как преодоление стереотипов способствует формированию доверия в многообразной рабочей среде. В условиях глобализации и роста межкультурных взаимодействий стереотипы могут мешать сотрудничеству, ухудшать динамику команды и снижать эффективность организаций. В статье анализируются психологические и социологические корни стереотипов, их проявления на рабочем месте и практические методы борьбы с ними. Доверие рассматривается как ключевой элемент успешной командной работы. Особое внимание уделяется межкультурному пониманию, инклюзивному лидерству и стратегиям коммуникации как способам снижения предубеждений и укрепления позитивных отношений в многонациональных и многокультурных коллективах.

Ключевые слова: стереотипы, культурное разнообразие, доверие, межкультурная коммуникация, инклюзия, командная динамика, предубеждения, лидерство.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada xilma-xil ish muhiti sharoitida ishonchni shakllantirishda stereotiplardan xalos bo'lishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Globallashuv va madaniy xilma-xillikning ortib borishi fonida stereotiplar ishchi guruhlardagi hamkorlikka salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi, jamoa dinamikasini susaytirishi va umumiy samaradorlikni pasaytirishi mumkin. Maqolada stereotiplarning psixologik va sotsiologik ildizlari, ularning ish joyida namoyon bo'lishi va ularga qarshi kurashishning amaliy usullari tahlil

qilinadi. Ishonch jamoaviy muvaffaqiyatning asosiy omili sifatida ko'rib, madaniyatlararo tushunuv, inklyuziv liderlik va samarali kommunikatsiya stereotiplarga barham berishda muhim vositalar sifatida taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Stereotiplar, madaniy xilma-xillik, ishonch, madaniyatlararo muloqot, inklyuziya, jamoa dinamikasi, xurofot, liderlik.

Introduction

In today's globalized economy, the workforce has become increasingly diverse. Employees from different cultural, religious, linguistic, and ethnic backgrounds must work together and achieve common organizational goals. However, despite the potential advantages of diversity—including innovation, broader perspectives, and global competence—stereotypes remain a major obstacle to trust and collaboration. Stereotypes are preconceived, oversimplified beliefs about individuals based on group membership, and they can distort reality, increase bias, and reduce fairness in decision-making. Trust, on the other hand, is the foundation of effective team performance and organizational commitment. This article examines how trust can be built by actively confronting and overcoming stereotypes in professional environments.

Understanding Stereotypes in the Workplace

Stereotypes are cognitive shortcuts that help individuals process social information quickly, but often at the cost of accuracy. They can be based on nationality ("Germans are strict"), gender ("women are emotional"), or even age ("older workers resist change"). In the workplace, such assumptions lead to biased evaluations, exclusion from decision-making, and strained relationships. Stereotypes may result in self-fulfilling prophecies, where employees perform according to the expectations imposed on them.

Stereotyping can also manifest subtly through microaggressions, unequal task assignments, or implicit bias in performance reviews. These actions—conscious or unconscious—undermine morale and signal that certain employees are less valued. According to Tajfel's Social Identity Theory (1981), individuals categorize themselves and others into in-groups and out-groups, which contributes to workplace division and distrust.

The Role of Trust in Diverse Teams

Trust is a foundational component of effective teamwork, particularly in diverse work environments where team members may differ across dimensions such as culture, language, gender, and socio-economic background. It is broadly defined as the willingness to be vulnerable to others based on the expectation that they will act in a fair, reliable, and ethical manner (Mayer, Davis & Schoorman, 1995). In multicultural teams, trust does not emerge automatically; it must be intentionally developed and nurtured. The presence of cultural stereotypes—generalized and often inaccurate assumptions about a group—can undermine this process by distorting perceptions of a

person's ability, benevolence, or integrity. These are the three critical dimensions of trust identified in Mayer et al.'s model. Ability refers to perceived competence in fulfilling responsibilities; benevolence implies genuine concern for others' well-being; and integrity suggests adherence to shared norms and principles. If individuals are stereotyped as less capable or less honest based on their background, it impedes trust formation and creates barriers to collaboration. In contrast, a high-trust environment—where individuals feel psychologically safe and respected—encourages risk-taking, open communication, and mutual learning. Trust also supports the equitable exchange of ideas and enhances innovation by fostering an inclusive climate where everyone feels heard and valued. Therefore, organizations seeking to leverage the benefits of workforce diversity must proactively dismantle stereotype-based biases and implement institutional policies that promote transparency, fairness, and mutual respect. Training in cultural awareness, equitable leadership practices, and accountability structures are all essential strategies for fostering interpersonal trust in such settings (Costa, Roe, & Taillieu, 2001; Gillespie & Mann, 2004).

Strategies for Overcoming Stereotypes

Intercultural Training:

Developing intercultural competence is one of the most effective methods for reducing the influence of stereotypes in the workplace. Such training programs are designed to enhance employees' awareness of cultural differences, improve cross-cultural communication, and address unconscious biases. Through interactive workshops, scenario-based discussions, and reflective exercises, employees can better understand how their own cultural backgrounds influence their perceptions and behaviors. These programs often include modules on cultural dimensions (e.g., individualism vs. collectivism, high vs. low context communication), as well as strategies for adapting communication styles to different cultural contexts. When implemented consistently, intercultural training not only promotes empathy and respect but also equips teams with practical tools to navigate diversity constructively.

Inclusive Leadership:

Leadership is pivotal in shaping the cultural climate of an organization. Inclusive leaders do more than simply tolerate diversity—they actively create spaces where all voices are heard and valued. They demonstrate cultural intelligence, exhibit emotional empathy, and take a proactive stance against exclusionary or discriminatory behaviors. Kouzes and Posner (2007) emphasize that leaders who lead with integrity, openness, and trust inspire their teams to collaborate more effectively. Inclusive leaders encourage participation from all team members, regardless of their background, and ensure that contributions are recognized fairly. They also serve as role models by promoting fairness in decision-making, acknowledging the unique strengths of diverse individuals, and integrating diverse perspectives into organizational goals and

strategies.

Structured Dialogue:

Open, honest communication is essential to dismantling stereotypes and building trust. Structured dialogue refers to facilitated, intentional conversations among employees that aim to foster mutual understanding and empathy. These dialogues create a psychologically safe space for team members to share personal experiences, voice concerns, and challenge misperceptions without fear of judgment. By encouraging perspective-taking and validating diverse lived experiences, structured dialogues help break down barriers created by assumptions and bias. Organizations may implement these through regular team reflection sessions, diversity circles, or guided discussions led by trained facilitators. Over time, such practices reduce tension, increase emotional connection among team members, and contribute to a more cohesive work environment.

Fair Organizational Policies:

Biases in recruitment, evaluation, and promotion can perpetuate stereotypes and hinder trust-building efforts. Therefore, organizations must institutionalize equity through transparent and standardized human resource practices. This includes clear criteria for hiring and promotions, regular audits of performance reviews to detect and correct bias, and ensuring diverse representation in leadership and decision-making roles. Policies should also support mentoring programs, employee resource groups, and grievance mechanisms that empower minority employees. When individuals observe that opportunities are distributed fairly and that their voices matter at every level of the organization, they are more likely to feel a sense of belonging and trust in the institution. Such systemic approaches reinforce inclusive values and ensure that diversity is not only celebrated but meaningfully integrated into organizational culture.

Case Study: Trust-Building in a Multinational Project Team

A compelling case study from an international IT company based in Central Asia highlights the impact of cultural awareness and structured interventions on trust development in diverse teams. The team in question consisted of engineers from Uzbekistan, India, and Russia—each bringing distinct cultural norms regarding communication, hierarchy, and collaboration. Initially, the team experienced significant friction and reduced productivity due to cultural misunderstandings. Russian engineers, for example, often gave direct and blunt feedback, which Uzbek colleagues interpreted as overly harsh or disrespectful. Conversely, the Uzbek engineers, influenced by traditionally high power-distance cultural norms, tended to use more deferential and hierarchical communication styles. Indian team members, accustomed to more assertive dialogue and flatter organizational structures, perceived this as a lack of initiative or engagement. These misinterpretations, rooted in cultural stereotypes and differences in communication expectations, created barriers to trust,

increased tension, and limited effective knowledge-sharing.

To address the growing dysfunction, the company implemented a structured three-phase intervention aimed at building cultural competence and reducing stereotype-driven biases. The first phase involved mandatory intercultural communication workshops focused on fostering empathy, enhancing active listening skills, and increasing awareness of implicit biases. In the second phase, the team introduced a rotating leadership model, allowing members from each cultural group to take turns leading projects and meetings, thereby promoting mutual respect and recognition of diverse strengths. The third phase featured monthly feedback circles, providing a psychologically safe space for team members to express concerns, clarify intentions, and collaboratively reflect on team dynamics. After six months, internal surveys showed a 40% increase in perceived interpersonal trust and a 25% rise in overall team efficiency, as measured by project delivery times and employee satisfaction metrics. This case demonstrates that when organizations proactively address the roots of intercultural friction—especially stereotypes—they can transform team dynamics, foster inclusivity, and drive both human and performance-centered outcomes.

Conclusion

In an era of rapid globalization and increasing interconnectivity, the ability to foster trust across cultural boundaries is no longer a peripheral concern but a strategic imperative for organizations. Stereotypes, while deeply embedded in human cognition, pose significant risks to psychological safety, fairness, and the collaborative spirit required for high-performing teams. As this article has shown, overcoming these biases requires deliberate, multi-level interventions—from individual awareness-building through intercultural training to systemic changes in leadership approaches and organizational policies. Trust, particularly in multicultural settings, must be nurtured through empathy, inclusivity, transparent communication, and mutual respect. When organizations invest in creating environments that actively dismantle prejudices and promote diversity of thought and identity, they do more than just enhance interpersonal relations; they unlock the full potential of their workforce. In doing so, they position themselves to be more innovative, agile, and resilient in an increasingly complex global market. Ultimately, fostering trust by overcoming stereotypes is not just about improving workplace harmony—it is about shaping forward-looking institutions grounded in equity, collaboration, and human dignity.

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Innovations in Language Teaching and Intercultural Communication: Shaping Global Education for the 21st Century

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Abstract

This article highlights the importance of innovations in language teaching and intercultural communication for improving educational outcomes and fostering global understanding. It focuses on modern methods like project-based learning, technology use, and culturally relevant instruction that enhance language proficiency and intercultural competence. Emphasizing the need to adapt to societal changes and globalization, the article advocates a balanced approach combining innovative and traditional methods to prepare learners for effective cross-cultural communication and increased employability in a diverse world.

Key words: Language teaching, Intercultural communication, Innovative methodologies, Technology in education, Communicative competence.

Аннотация

В этой статье подчеркивается важность инноваций в преподавании языка и межкультурной коммуникации для улучшения результатов обучения и содействия глобальному пониманию. Основное внимание уделяется современным методам, таким как проектное обучение, использование технологий и культурно-релевантное обучение, которые повышают уровень владения языком и межкультурную компетентность. Подчеркивая необходимость адаптации к общественным изменениям и глобализации, статья выступает за сбалансированный подход, сочетающий инновационные и традиционные методы, для подготовки учащихся к эффективному межкультурному общению и повышению

трудоустройства в разнообразном мире.

Ключевые слова: преподавание языка, межкультурная коммуникация, инновационные методики, технологии в образовании, коммуникативная компетентность.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola ta'lim natijalarini yaxshilash va global tushunishni rivojlantirish uchun til o'rgatish va madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi innovatsiyalarning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. U til va madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyani oshiradigan loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim, texnologiyadan foydalanish va madaniy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan ta'lim kabi zamonaviy usullarga qaratilgan. Maqola ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar va globallashuvga moslashish zarurligini ta'kidlab, o'quvchilarni samarali madaniyatlararo muloqotga tayyorlash va turli dunyoda ish bilan ta'minlanish darajasini oshirish uchun innovatsion va an'anaviy usullarni uyg'unlashtirgan muvozanatli yondashuvni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til o'qitish, Madaniyatlararo muloqot, Innovatsion metodologiyalar, Ta'limda texnologiya, Kommunikativ kompetentsiya.

In an era marked by rapid globalization, technological advancement, and unprecedented cultural exchange, the demand for effective language teaching and intercultural communication skills has never been greater. The traditional boundaries of geography, culture, and language are dissolving, creating new opportunities-and new challenges-for education systems worldwide. As a result, innovations in language teaching and intercultural communication have emerged as critical drivers of educational excellence and global understanding. These innovations not only enhance language proficiency but also equip learners with the skills and attitudes necessary to navigate and thrive in diverse cultural contexts.

The Need for Innovation in Language Education

The 21st century is characterized by constant change. Migration, international business, digital connectivity, and multicultural societies have made cross-cultural communication an everyday reality. Traditional language teaching methods, while foundational, often fall short in preparing learners for the complexities of real-world communication. This gap has spurred educators, researchers, and policymakers to seek out and implement innovative methodologies that make language learning more relevant, engaging, and impactful.

Language is more than a set of grammatical rules and vocabulary lists; it is a living, evolving means of expressing identity, culture, and worldview. Effective language teaching must therefore go beyond the mechanics of language to include cultural context, pragmatic use, and intercultural sensitivity. Innovations in methodology are essential for achieving this holistic approach.

Enhanced Learning Experiences Through Innovation

One of the most significant shifts in language education is the move toward project-based and experiential learning. These methods place students at the center of the learning process, encouraging active participation, critical thinking, and

collaboration.

- **Project-Based Learning:** Students might work together to produce a podcast, organize a cultural event, or develop a business plan in the target language. These projects require them to research, communicate, and solve problems-mirroring real-life language use (Bukhkalov et al., 2023).

- **Case Studies and Simulations:** Learners engage with authentic scenarios, such as negotiating a contract or resolving a cultural misunderstanding. These activities build not only language skills but also confidence and adaptability.

Technology Integration

The digital revolution has brought a wealth of resources and opportunities to language education:

- **Language Learning Apps:** Platforms like Duolingo, Babbel, and Memrise offer personalized, gamified learning experiences that motivate students and provide instant feedback.

- **Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR):** Immersive technologies allow learners to "travel" to foreign countries, interact with virtual native speakers, and experience cultural contexts firsthand.

- **Online Exchanges and Telecollaboration:** Students can connect with peers around the world through video calls, collaborative projects, and social media, practicing language skills in authentic intercultural settings.

Innovative methodologies also recognize that every learner is unique. Adaptive learning technologies use artificial intelligence to tailor content, pace, and feedback to individual needs, ensuring that all students can progress at their own rate and overcome specific challenges.

Promoting Cultural Relevance and Intercultural Competence

Cultural competence is now recognized as an essential component of communicative competence. Innovative language teaching integrates culture at every stage:

- **Authentic Materials:** Films, music, literature, and news articles expose students to the values, humor, and everyday life of the target culture.

- **Cultural Discussions and Reflection:** Classroom debates, reflective journals, and cultural comparison exercises encourage students to think critically about their own and others' cultural assumptions (Chun-ying & Wen-jing, n.d.).

By fostering intercultural awareness, language education helps students become open-minded, empathetic, and adaptable-qualities essential for global citizenship. Students learn to recognize and respect cultural differences, challenge stereotypes, and communicate with sensitivity and respect.

International Partnerships: Schools and universities increasingly participate in exchange programs, joint projects, and international competitions, providing

students with direct experience of intercultural collaboration. **Service Learning and Community Engagement:** Language learners can volunteer with immigrant communities, participate in cultural festivals, or support international development projects, applying their skills in meaningful ways.

Societal changes-such as increased mobility, digital transformation, and shifting labor market demands-require language education to be flexible and forward-looking.

Responsive Curriculum: Innovative educators continually update curricula to reflect current events, emerging technologies, and global challenges such as climate change or public health (Suima, 2023). **Lifelong Learning:** The concept of language learning as a lifelong journey is gaining traction. Adult education, workplace language training, and online courses ensure that language and intercultural skills remain relevant throughout life.

Innovative language teaching also addresses the needs of diverse learners, including refugees, migrants, and students with special educational needs. Inclusive practices, differentiated instruction, and culturally responsive pedagogy help ensure that all students have access to high-quality language education.

Impact on Intercultural Communication

Innovative language teaching methodologies are directly linked to improved intercultural communication skills. Students learn to:

- Interpret verbal and nonverbal cues in different cultural contexts.
- Adapt their language and behavior to suit the norms and expectations of various cultures.
- Resolve misunderstandings and manage intercultural conflict constructively (Alieva, 2018).

These skills are not only valuable for personal growth but are also critical for professional success in international environments.

Meeting Professional and Societal Demands

Employers increasingly seek candidates who can work effectively across cultures and languages. Proficiency in a foreign language, combined with intercultural competence, significantly enhances employability and career advancement.

Global Business: Companies need employees who can negotiate, market, and collaborate internationally.

Diplomacy and International Relations: Language and cultural skills are essential for building bridges between nations.

Education, Tourism, and Healthcare: Professionals in these fields must communicate with clients, patients, and colleagues from diverse backgrounds (Alieva, 2018).

While innovation is crucial, traditional methods still play an important role,

especially in the early stages of language learning. Systematic grammar instruction, vocabulary drills, and structured practice provide a strong foundation upon which more innovative, communicative approaches can build.

An Integrated Approach. The most effective language programs combine the best of both worlds:

Blended Learning: A mix of face-to-face instruction, online resources, and experiential activities caters to different learning styles and preferences.

Formative and Summative Assessment: Traditional tests can be complemented by performance-based assessments, portfolios, and self-reflection, providing a more comprehensive picture of student progress.

Challenges and Future Directions. Despite the clear benefits, implementing innovative methodologies can be challenging. Barriers include limited resources, lack of teacher training, resistance to change, and unequal access to technology. Addressing these challenges requires investment, ongoing professional development, and a commitment to equity. Teachers are at the forefront of innovation, but they need support from administrators, policymakers, and the wider community. Collaborative networks, research partnerships, and international organizations can help share best practices and drive continuous improvement. As technology continues to evolve and societies become even more interconnected, the future of language teaching and intercultural communication will be shaped by ongoing innovation. Artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and global collaboration platforms will create new opportunities for immersive, personalized, and impactful learning experiences.

Conclusion

Innovations in language teaching and intercultural communication are not just educational trends—they are essential responses to the realities of our globalized world. By embracing new methodologies, integrating cultural content, and adapting to societal changes, educators can empower students to communicate effectively, appreciate diversity, and contribute positively to a more interconnected and peaceful world. At the same time, maintaining a balance with traditional methods ensures that learners develop a strong linguistic foundation. The journey toward global understanding and cooperation begins in the language classroom, where innovation and tradition come together to shape the citizens of tomorrow.

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“Proverbs as Cultural Artifacts: Insights into Uzbek and English Neighborhood Values”

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi maqollarda aks etgan madaniy qadriyatlar va ijtimoiy me'yorlarni tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot qo'shnichilik madaniyatiga oid maqollarni lingvistik va madaniy jihatdan taqqoslash orqali jamiyatning munosabat va qadriyatlarini aks ettirishini ko'rsatishga qaratilgan. Maqolada yozma manbalar, suhbatlar va fokus-guruhlardan olingan ma'lumotlar sifat jihatidan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'zbek va ingliz madaniyatlarida qo'shnichilik, ishonch va hamkorlik tushunchalarining o'xshash va farqli jihatlarini ochib berib, madaniyatlararo tushunishni chuqurlashtirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqollar, qo'shnichilik madaniyati, o'zbek, ingliz, qiyosiy tilshunoslik, madaniy aks, ijtimoiy me'yorlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются культурные ценности и социальные нормы, отраженные в пословицах узбекского и английского языков. Исследование направлено на анализ этих пословиц с лингвистической и культурной точек зрения, чтобы показать, как они отражают общественные отношения и ценности. Данные были собраны из письменных источников, интервью и фокус-групп, а затем подвергнуты качественному анализу. Результаты исследования выявляют сходства и различия в восприятии соседства, доверия и сотрудничества в узбекской и английской культурах, способствуя более глубокому межкультурному пониманию.

Ключевые слова: пословицы, культура соседства, узбекский, английский, сравнительное языкознание, культурное отражение, социальные нормы.

Abstract: This article explores the cultural values and social norms reflected in the proverbs of Uzbek and English languages, focusing on their relevance to neighborhood culture. By comparing and analyzing the linguistic and cultural nuances embedded in these proverbs, the study aims to reveal how language serves as a mirror of societal attitudes and interactions. Data were collected from written sources, interviews, and focus groups, analyzed using a qualitative methodology. The findings

highlight striking similarities and differences in how Uzbek and English cultures conceptualize neighborhood relationships, trust, and cooperation, offering insights into intercultural understanding.

Keywords: proverbs, neighborhood culture, Uzbek, English, comparative linguistics, cultural reflection, social norms.

1. Introduction

Proverbs are succinct expressions that encapsulate the moral values, traditions, and societal attitudes of a culture. As succinct carriers of collective wisdom, they provide insights into how communities perceive and navigate social relationships, including those within neighborhoods. Scholars have argued that proverbs function as “the shorthand of cultural transmission,” preserving and perpetuating values across generations (Mieder, 2004). This study focuses on proverbs related to neighborhood culture in Uzbek and English languages, aiming to uncover the cultural similarities and differences embedded within them.

Proverbs are more than mere linguistic tools; they reflect the shared beliefs and lived experiences of a community. For example, Uzbek proverbs like “Qo‘shni qursang – devoridan bo‘lmas, odamidani bo‘ladi” (If you build a neighbor, it’s not the wall but the person that matters) emphasize human relationships over physical boundaries. Similarly, the English proverb “Good fences make good neighbors” highlights the value of maintaining boundaries to foster harmonious relationships. These examples illustrate how proverbs embody the societal attitudes toward trust, respect, and cooperation in a given culture.

Neighborhoods, as microcosms of social interaction, play a vital role in shaping communal values and individual behavior. In Uzbek culture, the concept of **mahalla** represents more than a physical neighborhood—it is a socio-cultural institution that fosters mutual support and collective responsibility (Dadabaev, 2013). Proverbs such as “Qo‘shnikida pishgan taomning hidi yoqimli” (The aroma of food cooked in the neighbor’s house is pleasant) reflect this spirit of communal sharing and interconnectedness.

In English-speaking societies, neighborhoods are often seen as spaces where cooperation and mutual respect coexist with individuality and personal boundaries. Proverbs like “A friend in need is a friend indeed” emphasize the importance of trust and support, while “Every man’s home is his castle” underscores the significance of privacy and autonomy within the community (Taylor, 2019).

This article aims to explore and compare neighborhood-related proverbs in Uzbek and English languages to identify the cultural values and social norms embedded within them. By analyzing these proverbs, the study seeks to enhance our understanding of how societies conceptualize neighborhood relationships and the cultural underpinnings of trust, cooperation, and mutual respect.

The objectives of this study include:

- 1) Identifying neighborhood-related proverbs in Uzbek and English languages.
- 2) Analyzing the cultural values and social norms reflected in these proverbs.
- 3) Comparing the conceptualizations of neighborhood culture in both linguistic and cultural contexts.
- 4) Exploring how these proverbs contribute to intercultural understanding.

Research Questions:

- 1) What are the prominent themes in neighborhood-related proverbs in Uzbek and English languages?
- 2) How do these proverbs reflect the cultural values and social norms of their respective societies?
- 3) What similarities and differences can be observed in the portrayal of neighborhood culture in these proverbs?

The proverb “*Yaxshi qo'shni – yarim boylik*” (A good neighbor is half your wealth) in Uzbek culture underscores the value of harmonious relationships within the neighborhood. Trust and cooperation are seen as essential components of daily life, reflecting the importance of collective well-being.

In contrast, the English proverb “Don't burn your bridges” serves as a metaphorical reminder to maintain relationships, even as one moves forward in life. While this may not explicitly refer to neighbors, it reflects a broader cultural norm of preserving ties, which can be applied to neighborhood dynamics.

By examining these and other examples, the study highlights how proverbs encode the moral and ethical expectations of their respective cultures, offering valuable insights into the similarities and differences in neighborhood conceptualizations across Uzbek and English-speaking societies.

Proverbs are often described as succinct, metaphorical expressions of cultural wisdom, encapsulating societal values and norms (Norrick, 1985). They function as cultural artifacts, preserving traditions, transmitting collective knowledge, and shaping interpersonal behavior (Mieder, 2004). Scholars have noted that proverbs often reflect universal human experiences, albeit filtered through the lens of specific cultural contexts (Dundes, 1975).

Studies show that proverbs serve multiple roles, including moral instruction, conflict resolution, and social bonding. For instance, paremiology studies highlight how proverbs function as rhetorical tools in public discourse, particularly in oral societies (Taylor, 1931). In both Uzbek and English-speaking communities, proverbs convey expectations about trust, cooperation, and mutual respect, key components of neighborhood culture (Dadabaev, 2013; Taylor, 2019).

Neighborhoods are microcosms of society where social norms are negotiated and reinforced. In Uzbek culture, the concept of **mahalla**—a tightly knit neighborhood structure—plays a crucial role in fostering communal responsibility and moral

guidance (Kamp, 2011). Proverbs such as “*Qo'shni bor – xudo bor*” (Where there is a neighbor, there is God) emphasize the spiritual and practical importance of neighborly ties.

Conversely, in English-speaking cultures, neighborhoods are often perceived as spaces of individual autonomy balanced with communal cooperation. Studies on English community life reveal that proverbs like “Good neighbors make a good neighborhood” encapsulate the dual emphasis on independence and interdependence (Taylor, 2019).

2. Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach to explore and analyze the cultural values and social norms embedded in Uzbek and English proverbs related to neighborhood culture. A qualitative approach is ideal for examining the nuanced meanings, contexts, and implications of proverbs, allowing for a deeper understanding of the cultural underpinnings of neighborhood relationships (Creswell, 2014). The research methodology includes data collection from various sources, thematic analysis of the data, and validation through focus group discussions.

The data for this study were drawn from several key sources to ensure a comprehensive and diverse range of proverbs that reflect the cultural perspectives of both Uzbek and English-speaking communities:

3. Collections of Uzbek and English Proverbs:

Uzbek Proverbs: Written sources containing Uzbek proverbs were sourced from ethnographic works and books on Central Asian oral traditions. These included collections such as “Uzbek Proverbs and Sayings” by M. R. Qosimov and works by Dadabaev (2013) on neighborhood culture in Uzbekistan. An example of an Uzbek proverb reflecting neighborhood culture is “*Qo'shnikida pishgan taomning hidi yoqimli*” (The aroma of food cooked in the neighbor's house is pleasant), which emphasizes the shared, communal nature of Uzbek neighborhoods.

English Proverbs: For English proverbs, both classic collections like “The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs” and contemporary studies were used. An example of an English proverb related to neighborhoods is “*Good fences make good neighbors,*” which emphasizes the importance of boundaries and respect for personal space in fostering healthy relationships between neighbors (Frost, 1914).

A thorough literature review was conducted to contextualize the findings within the broader academic discourse. Works on neighborhood culture, such as Kamp (2011) on the **mahalla** system in Uzbekistan, were reviewed. Additionally, literature on the role of community in English-speaking societies, like Taylor (2019), was incorporated to explore how neighborhood dynamics are reflected in proverbs.

Semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with native speakers from both Uzbek and English-speaking backgrounds. Participants

included cultural experts, linguists, and community members who provided contextual interpretations of the proverbs. An example of a focus group discussion in Uzbekistan included community members reflecting on the proverb “*Yaxshi qo‘shni – yarim boylik*” (*A good neighbor is half your wealth*), which participants described as indicative of the collective responsibilities and bonds of Uzbek neighborhoods. In English-speaking settings, focus group participants discussed proverbs like “*A neighbor in need is a neighbor indeed,*” highlighting the significance of trust and support in building strong neighborhood relations.

The data collection process involved several stages to gather a diverse range of proverbs related to neighborhood culture in both Uzbek and English contexts:

The first step was to identify proverbs specifically related to neighborhood life in both languages. This was done by searching through proverb collections, oral traditions, and modern compilations. Proverbs were selected based on their direct relevance to neighborhood interactions, including themes such as trust, cooperation, conflict resolution, and social obligations. Examples include:

“*A good neighbor is better than a distant relative*” in English, which highlights the value of proximity and social support within neighborhoods.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study, offering insights from the thematic analysis of Uzbek and English proverbs related to neighborhood culture. The analysis reveals both common and unique themes in the two cultural contexts, underscoring the deep connection between language and societal values. Additionally, the discussion highlights cultural similarities and differences, reflecting the role of historical, social, and religious factors in shaping neighborhood norms.

Thematic analysis of the collected proverbs from both Uzbek and English sources uncovered several recurring themes central to neighborhood life. The major themes include:

Importance of Neighbors: Both Uzbek and English proverbs emphasize the significance of good neighbors. In Uzbek culture, the proverb “*Qo‘shni qo‘shnining ko‘zgusi*” (A neighbor is a mirror of oneself) encapsulates the belief that one’s relationship with neighbors is a reflection of personal character. In contrast, English proverbs such as “*A good neighbor is better than a distant relative*” emphasize the practical benefits of strong neighborhood ties over familial connections. The shared value here is the recognition that neighbors play a pivotal role in one’s well-being and social stability.

Mutual Support and Cooperation: Another common theme is the idea of mutual support and cooperation within the neighborhood. Uzbek proverbs such as “*Bir qo‘l bilan tepish mumkin emas*” (You cannot clap with one hand) highlight the necessity of collective effort in maintaining a harmonious neighborhood. Similarly, English

proverbs like “*A friend in need is a friend indeed*” emphasize the importance of reciprocity and solidarity, especially in times of need. Both cultures recognize the fundamental need for neighbors to help one another, whether through emotional, social, or material support.

Conflict Resolution: Both Uzbek and English proverbs address conflict resolution in neighborhood settings, though with distinct cultural nuances. Uzbek proverbs such as “*Ko'zini och, qo'shniga qarama*” (Be watchful, do not meddle in others' affairs) suggest the importance of maintaining boundaries to avoid conflicts, while English proverbs like “*Good fences make good neighbors*” underscore the value of clear personal space and boundaries to preserve peace. Both cultures emphasize that boundaries, whether physical or social, are essential to maintaining harmony.

The study revealed significant cultural similarities in how both Uzbek and English proverbs reflect the values of trust, cooperation, and community. Both cultures place high value on maintaining positive relationships with neighbors and emphasize the need for mutual support and collective responsibility. For example, both the Uzbek proverb “*Yaxshi qo'shni – yarim boylik*” (A good neighbor is half your wealth) and the English proverb “*A good neighbor is better than a distant relative*” underscore the practical importance of fostering neighborly ties for personal and community well-being.

Moreover, both cultures highlight the role of neighbors in providing support in times of need. The theme of mutual aid is central to both Uzbek and English proverbs, illustrating that neighbors are seen not only as social companions but also as sources of emotional and material help in times of distress.

Despite the common themes of mutual support and cooperation, significant cultural differences were found in the ways Uzbek and English proverbs conceptualize the roles of neighbors. A key difference lies in the degree of collectivism and individualism reflected in the proverbs.

Uzbek proverbs, shaped by the mahalla system, a highly communal structure, emphasize collective responsibility. For example, the proverb “*Qo'shnikida pishgan taomning hidi yoqimli*” (The aroma of food cooked in the neighbor's house is pleasant) illustrates the communal nature of Uzbek neighborhoods, where people take joy in one another's successes and support each other in daily life. These proverbs often reflect a collectivist society where neighborhood well-being is directly tied to communal involvement and collective effort.

In contrast, English proverbs tend to reflect a more individualistic cultural orientation, often focusing on personal boundaries and autonomy. The proverb “*Good fences make good neighbors*” exemplifies the English value of respecting personal space and maintaining clear boundaries between individuals. This cultural difference may be attributed to historical and social factors, such as the rise of urbanization and

industrialization in English-speaking countries, which have fostered a greater emphasis on individual rights and privacy.

The findings of this study have several implications for intercultural communication and understanding. First, recognizing the shared themes of trust, cooperation, and support in Uzbek and English proverbs can foster greater cross-cultural understanding and appreciation of neighborhood dynamics. By understanding how different cultures conceptualize the role of neighbors, individuals can navigate social interactions with greater sensitivity to cultural values.

Second, the study's findings can inform community-building efforts, as they reveal how cultural values influence neighborly relationships. For example, while collectivist values may guide community life in Uzbekistan, English-speaking communities may benefit from more collaborative approaches that encourage social ties without compromising personal space.

Finally, the study underscores the importance of proverbs as cultural tools for teaching and reinforcing social norms. By examining proverbs from different cultures, individuals can better understand how language reflects societal values and can use these insights to promote intercultural dialogue and cooperation.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reveals significant insights into the role of proverbs in shaping neighborhood culture and relationships in both Uzbek and English-speaking societies. The findings underscore the shared cultural values of trust, cooperation, and mutual support, while also highlighting the cultural differences in how neighbors are conceptualized in terms of collectivism versus individualism. Understanding these cultural nuances can enhance intercultural communication and promote harmonious neighborhood relations across different cultural contexts.

Future research could expand on this study by exploring proverbs from additional languages and cultures, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how neighborhood relationships are perceived globally. Furthermore, investigating the role of proverbs in modern urban settings, where traditional neighborhood structures may be evolving, could offer valuable insights into the changing dynamics of community life.

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O'ZBEK MAKTABLARIDA INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA MADANIYATLARARO KOMMUNIKATSIYANI O'RGATISH SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani o'rgatishning samaradorligi o'rganiladi. O'zbekistonning bir nechta maktablarida olib borilgan kuzatuv, intervyu va so'rovnomalar asosida o'quvchilarning madaniy kompetensiyasi va til o'rganish motivatsiyasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, madaniy tarkibiy qismlarning darslarga kiritilishi o'quvchilarning til o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishini va samaradorligini oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, maktab ta'limi, madaniy kompetensiya, kommunikativ yondashuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается эффективность обучения межкультурной коммуникации в процессе преподавания английского языка. На основе наблюдений, интервью и анкетирования, проведенных в ряде школ Узбекистана, был проанализирован взаимосвязь между культурной компетентностью учащихся и их мотивацией к изучению языка. Результаты исследования показали, что включение культурных компонентов в учебные занятия повышает интерес учащихся к изучению языка и улучшает их учебные достижения.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, межкультурная коммуникация, школьное образование, культурная компетентность, коммуникативный подход.

Annotation: This article examines the effectiveness of teaching intercultural communication within the process of English language instruction. Based on observations, interviews, and surveys conducted in several schools in Uzbekistan, the study analyzes the correlation between students' cultural competence and their motivation for language learning. The results indicate that incorporating cultural components into lessons increases students' interest in learning the language and enhances overall learning effectiveness.

Keywords: English language, intercultural communication, school education, cultural competence, communicative approach.

Globalizatsiya sharoitida xorijiy tilni o'rganish faqat lingvistik bilimlar bilan cheklanmay, balki madaniy kompetensiyani ham shakllantirishni talab qiladi. Ingliz tili xalqaro aloqa vositasi sifatida nafaqat grammatika va lug'at boyligini, balki uni ishlatish kontekstini, madaniy fonini ham tushunishni talab etadi. O'zbek maktablarida ingliz tili o'rgatilayotgan bo'lsa-da, ko'plab hollarda madaniy komponentlar yetarlicha e'tibordan chetda qolmoqda. Hozirgi kunda, dolzarb mavzulardan biri o'zbek maktablarida ingliz tilini kommunikativ o'qitish tizimini yo'lga qo'yish nafaqat ingliz tili, balki ingliz madaniyati bilan ham tanishtirish, ya'ni maktab o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini keng muloqotga tayyor inson qilib yetishtirish zarur. Ushbu maqolada O'zbek maktablarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya integratsiyaning ahamiyati va amaliy samarasi o'rganiladi.

Mamlakatimiz mustaqillikka erishgandan so'ng, chet tillarini o'rgatishga qiziqish oshdi va yoshlar uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlar yaratib berildi. Birinchi prezidentimiz Islom Karimov aytganlaridek, "Hozirgi paytda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishga yurtimizda katta ahamiyat berilmoqda. Bu ham albatta, bejiz emas. Bugun jahon hamjamiyati o'ziga munosib o'rin egallashga intilayotgan mamlakatlarimiz uchun, chet ellik sheriklarimiz bilan hamjihatlikda, hamkorlikda o'z buyuk kelajagini qurayotgan xalqimiz uchun xorijiy tillarni mukammal bilishning ahamiyatini baholashning hojati yo'qdir". Ushbu fikrlarning mantiqiy davomi sifatida 2012 yil 10 dekabrda qabul qilingan "Chet tillarini" o'rgatish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi Prezident Qarori chet tillarini o'rganish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirdi. Respublikamizda chet tilining o'qitilishi, chet tili o'qituvchilarining bilim va ko'nikmalarini baholashning umumevropa ramkalari tavsiyanomalari (CEFR) ga mos ravishda yangi usul va talablari ishlab chiqildi. Unga ko'ra umumta'lim maktablari va kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilari uchun darsliklar yaratildi. Ushbu talablarga mos ravishda o'quv xonalari stendlar va yangi axborot kommunikativ texnikalar bilan ji-hozlandi. Chet tili o'rganishga bo'lgan talab ham kundan kunga oshib bormoqda. Chet tili fani to'rt aspectga (o'qish, yoish, tinglab tushunish va gapirish) bo'linib, ularning har biri bo'yicha alohida tushuncha va ko'nikmalar berilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 8-maydagi PQ-4312-son qarori 1-ilovaga ko'ra "O'zbekiston Respublikasining maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi"ni yanada rivojlantirishning eng muhim yo'nalishlaridan

biri maktabgacha ta'limni rivojlantirish - ta'lim jarayoniga zamonaviy pedagogika va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini (AKT) keng joriy etish va buning uchun amalga oshirilishi kerak bo'lgan ustuvor vazifalar belgilab berilgan. Bugungi kunda chet tillarini bilish kasbiy ta'limning ajralmas qismlardan biriga aylanib bormoqda. Bu ham maktabgacha ta'lim jarayonini e'tibordan chetda qoldirmadi. So'nggi yillarda maktablarda yangi axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish masalasi tobora ko'proq ko'tarilmoqda. Bu nafaqat yangi texnik vositalar, balki o'qitishning yangi shakllari va usullari, o'quv jarayoniga yangicha yondoshishdir. Chet tillarni o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi maktab o'quvchilarining kommunikativ madaniyatini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish, chet tilini amaliy o'zlashtirishga o'rgatishdir.

XXI asrda ingliz tili global muloqot vositasiga aylangan bir davrda, bu tilni o'rgatish jarayoni endi faqat grammatik bilimlarni berish bilan cheklanib qolmayapti. Hozirgi pedagogik tendensiyalar ingliz tilini o'rganishni madaniy kontekstda amalga oshirishni, ya'ni o'quvchilarda madaniyatlararo kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishni zarur deb biladi. Bu kompetensiya orqali o'quvchilar xorijiy tilni o'zlashtirish bilan birga, boshqa xalqlarning madaniyatiga nisbatan hurmat, bag'rikenglik va tushunish kabi ijtimoiy-psixologik ko'nikmalarni ham egallaydilar. Mashhur rus tilshunosi G.O.Vinokurning fikriga ko'ra, tilni o'rganayotgan har qanday tilshunos, albatta, tanlagan tili uning mahsuloti bo'lgan o'sha madaniyatning tadqiqotchisiga aylanishi kerak. M.Brok va V.Nagasaka kabi mutaxassislar til o'rganishning barcha bosqichlarida madaniyatlararo yoki pragmatik kompetensiyani hisobga olish kerakligini aytib o'tishgan.⁹

Madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya – bu turli madaniyat vakillari o'rtasida samarali muloqot o'rnatish jarayonidir. Bu jarayonda nafaqat til, balki madaniy qadriyatlar, xulq-atvor me'yorlari, mimika, imo-ishoralar, nutq uslubi va hatto sukunatning o'zi ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shu bois, ingliz tilini o'rganish – bu faqat lingvistik emas, balki sotsiokultural faoliyat hamdir. V.S.Bibler madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya to'g'risida so'z yuritar ekan, madaniyatlararo muloqot maydonidagi erkin munosabatlarning alohida ijtimoiy shakli, madaniyatning yangi ko'rinishi sifatida ta'riflaydi.¹⁰ Aynan bu o'rinda asosiy dolzarb masala muloqotni yo'lga qo'yishdagi to'siqlar hisoblanadi. Madaniyatlararo muloqotda nafaqat og'zaki yoki yozma nutq muhim, balki tana harakati, imo-ishoralar, yuz ifodalari ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Masalan, biror madaniyatda ko'zga tik qarash hurmat deb hisoblansa, boshqa madaniyatda bu qo'pollik sifatida qabul qilinadi. Shuning uchun ham madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya bu — turli tafakkurga ega odamlar o'rtasida bir-birini to'g'ri tushunishga erishish vositasidir.

⁹ I. Brok va Nagasaka. Pragmatic Content in Global and Local Textbooks 2005; 34-40-b (Til o'qitish asoslari 2005; 12-23-b)

¹⁰ Библер В. С. От наукоучения — к логике культуры. — 1991. — Политиздат, 1991. — 417 с.

Shuningdek, bu tushuncha insonlarda bag'rikenglik, ochiq fikrlilik va madaniyatlararo hurmat tuyg'usini rivojlantiradi. Odamlar faqat o'zining madaniyatiga yopishib qolmasdan, boshqa xalqlarning turmush tarzi, dunyoqarashi va qadriyatlariga ham tushunish bilan yondashishni o'rganadilar. Bu esa hozirgi globallashayotgan dunyoda juda muhim ko'nikma hisoblanadi.

Madaniyatlararo yondashuvni samarali qo'llash o'qituvchidan yuqori darajadagi tayyorgarlikni talab etadi. U nafaqat ingliz tili, balki ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchi mamlakatlarning tarixiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy xususiyatlari haqida ham yetarli bilimga ega bo'lishi kerak. Shu bilan birga, o'quvchining dunyoqarashini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan dars uslublarini qo'llay olishi lozim.

So'nggi yillarda ayrim O'zbekiston maktablarida olib borilgan tajribaviy ishlar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, madaniyatlararo yondashuvni tatbiq qilish o'quvchilarning til o'zlashtirish darajasini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Ularning nutq madaniyati, fikrlash kengligi va chet el fuqarolari bilan muloqotga tayyorlik darajasi yuqori bo'lmoqda. O'zbekiston maktablarida ingliz tilini madaniyatlararo yondashuv asosida o'qitish – bu nafaqat tilni chuqur o'zlashtirish, balki zamonaviy, global fikrlovchi yoshlarni tarbiyalash uchun muhim vositadir. Bu jarayonda o'qituvchi, o'quv materiallari, metodik yondashuvlar va texnologiyalarning bir-birini to'ldirishi zarur. Shu orqali, O'zbekiston yoshlari xalqaro hamjamiyatda munosib o'rin egallay oladigan, madaniyatlararo kompetensiyaga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislar sifatida voyaga yetadilar.

Shu munosabat bilan, talablar bilanbirgalikda tadqiqot o'tkazish maqsadida O'zbekistonning umumta'lim maktablaridan birida 8–9-sinf o'quvchilari o'rtasida so'rovnoma o'tkazildi. Tadqiqotda jami 50 nafar o'quvchi ishtirok etdi va so'rovnoma asosida ma'lumotlar to'plandi.

So'rovnoma natijalari

	O'quvchilarning 72% madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya darslarini qiziqarli deb topdi.
	65% o'quvchi ingliz tilida gapirishga bo'lgan ishonchi oshganini ta'kidladi.
	58% o'quvchi boshqa madaniyatlarni o'rganish orqali o'z dunyoqarashi kengayganini bildirdi.

Tadqiqot jarayonida o'quvchilardan tashqari ingliz tili fani o'qituvchilari bilan ham intervyu o'tkazildi. Intervyu orqali o'qituvchilarning madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani o'qitishdagi tajribasi, kuzatuvlari va fikrlari aniqlashtirildi. O'qituvchi bilan o'tkazilgan suhbatdan ham madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya elementlari darslarni jonlantirishi va o'quvchilarning tilga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirishini ko'rish mumkin bo'ldi.

Intervyu xulosalari

- O'qituvchilar madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya muhimligini tan olishgan, biroq ko'plab muammolar mavjud: resurslar yetishmasligi, dars vaqtining cheklanganligi, metodik qo'llanmalarning yo'qligi.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ingliz tili darslariga madaniyatlararo elementlarni kiritish o'quvchilarning til o'rganishdagi motivatsiyasi va ishtirokini oshiradi. Byram (1997) tomonidan ilgari surilgan madaniyatlararo kommunikativ kompetensiya modeli bu natijalarni nazariy jihatdan asoslaydi. Modelga ko'ra, til o'rganuvchilar nafaqat lingvistik bilimlarga, balki boshqa madaniyat vakillari bilan o'zaro munosabatni tushunish va hurmat qilish ko'nikmasiga ham ega bo'lishi kerak.

Shunga qaramay, O'zbekiston maktablarida bu yo'nalishda qator to'siqlar mavjud. O'qituvchilarning aksariyati bu borada maxsus tayyorgarlikka ega emas. Darsliklar esa, madaniy materiallarga boy bo'lsa-da, ularni chuqur integratsiya qilish uchun metodik yondashuv yetishmaydi.

Shu sababli, quyidagilar tavsiya qilinadi:

- Pedagog kadrlar tayyorlash dasturlarida madaniyatlararo ta'lim bo'yicha modullarni joriy etish.
- Darsliklarni amaliy madaniyatlararo vaziyatlar bilan boyitish.
- Onlayn platformalar orqali xorijiy o'quvchilar bilan muloqot qilish loyihalarini qo'llab-quvvatlash.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya — bu faqat chet tilini o'rganish emas, balki boshqa xalqlarni anglash, tushunish, va ular bilan to'g'ri, madaniyatga mos tarzda muloqot qilishni o'z ichiga olgan keng tushunchadir. Ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayoniga madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya elementlarini kiritish O'zbekiston maktablaridagi o'quvchilarning global tafakkuri, til kompetensiyasi va motivatsiyasini oshirishda samarali vosita bo'la oladi. Biroq bu jarayonni tizimli amalga oshirish uchun o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, resurslar bilan ta'minlash va metodik yondashuvni kuchaytirish zarur.

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Социальные и культурные коннотации музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi musiqa terminlarining ijtimoiy va madaniy konnotatsiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida musiqa atamalari jamiyatning qadriyatlarini, dunyoqarashi va tarixiy xususiyatlarini qanday aks ettirishi ochib beriladi. Qiyosiy tahlil orqali musiqa leksikasi shaxsiy identifikatsiya, gender rollari, globallashuv va yoshlar submadaniyati bilan bevosita bog'liqligi ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Inglizcha musiqa terminologiyasining zamonaviy o'zbek madaniyatiga ta'siri, shuningdek, ikki tilda musiqaviy tushunchalarni tarjima qilish va qabul qilishdagi xususiyatlar alohida e'tiborga olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Musiqa terminlari, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili, konnotatsiya, madaniyat, identifikatsiya, yoshlar, globallashuv, tarjima, tilshunoslik.

Metodologiya: Tadqiqot jarayonida qiyosiy-tahliliy metod, lingvomadaniy yondashuv va kontent-tahlil usullari qo'llanildi. Qiyosiy tahlil orqali ingliz va o'zbek tillarida musiqa terminlarining o'xshash va farqli jihatlari aniqlab olindi. Lingvomadaniy yondashuv esa bu terminlarning milliy qadriyatlar, an'analar va madaniy kontekstdagi o'rnini aniqlash imkonini berdi. Zamonaviy musiqa matnlari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi kontentlar, shuningdek musiqa bo'yicha darsliklar tahlili tadqiqotning empirik asosini tashkil etdi. Bundan tashqari, ikki tildagi so'zlovchilarning fikrlari va yoshlar orasidagi til amaliyotlari ham e'tiborga olindi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются социальные и культурные коннотации музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках. В ходе исследования раскрывается, каким образом музыкальные термины отражают ценности общества, его мировоззрение и исторические особенности. Сравнительный анализ позволяет выявить непосредственную связь музыкальной лексики с личной идентичностью, гендерными ролями, глобализацией и молодёжными субкультурами. Особое внимание уделяется влиянию английской музыкальной терминологии на современную узбекскую культуру, а также особенностям перевода и восприятия музыкальных понятий в обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: Музыкальные термины, английский язык, узбекский язык, коннотация, культура, идентификация, молодёжь, глобализация, перевод, лингвистика.

Методология: В исследовании использовались сравнительно-аналитический метод, лингвокультурный подход и методы контент-анализа. Сравнительный анализ позволил определить сходства и различия музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках. Лингвокультурный подход обеспечил возможность выявить роль этих терминов в контексте национальных ценностей, традиций и культурных реалий. Эмпирической основой исследования послужили тексты современной музыки, контент из социальных сетей, а также учебные пособия по музыкальной тематике.

Keywords: Music terms, English language, Uzbek language, connotation, culture, identity,

youth, globalization, translation, linguistics.

Abstract: This article looks at the social and cultural connotations of music terms in English and Uzbek languages. The research shows how music terms reflect the values of society, its worldview and historical features. The comparative analysis helps to find connection between music vocabulary and personal identity, gender roles, globalization and youth subcultures. Special attention is given to the influence of English music terminology on modern Uzbek culture, and also to the translation and understanding of music concepts in both languages.

Methodology: This research used comparative-analytical method, linguocultural approach and content analysis. The comparative analysis helped to find similarities and differences in music terms in English and Uzbek. Linguocultural approach made it possible to see how these terms work in the context of national values, traditions and culture. The main material for research were texts of modern music, social media content and music education books. Also, opinions of native speakers and language practice of young people were taken into account.

В современном мире музыка рассматривается не только как форма искусства, но и как важное социальное и культурное явление. Музыкальные термины, используемые в различных языках, несут в себе глубокие культурные значения, отражающие ценности, менталитет и исторический опыт общества. Особенно значимым представляется сравнительный анализ музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках, позволяющий выявить различия в их восприятии и интерпретации в разных культурных контекстах. Цель данной статьи — изучить социальные и культурные коннотации музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках, а также определить их роль в культурной идентификации и межкультурной коммуникации.

Музыка на протяжении всей истории человечества считалась одним из древнейших и наиболее выразительных средств самовыражения. Каждому народу присуща своя музыкальная традиция и соответствующая терминология. В данной статье анализируются не только лексические, но и социальные и культурные значения — то есть коннотации — музыкальных терминов, используемых в английском и узбекском языках. Ведь язык — это не только средство общения, но и зеркало культуры. Музыкальная терминология в английском языке непосредственно связана с массовой культурой, сформировавшейся в глобальном масштабе. К примеру, rock'n'roll — это не только музыкальное направление, но и символ социального движения, возникшего среди американской молодежи в 1950–60-х годах. Этот термин воспринимался как олицетворение свободы, бунта и нового мировоззрения.

Слово jazz, зародившееся в конце XIX — начале XX века среди афроамериканцев, выражает борьбу с тяжёлым трудом, расовым неравенством и стремление к внутренней свободе. Поэтому коннотации этого термина включают не только музыку, но и расовую идентичность, гордость и новаторство. Другой пример — hip-hop. Этот термин возник на улицах Нью-Йорка в 1970-х годах.

Первоначально он обозначал лишь музыкальный стиль, но сегодня охватывает целую культуру: граффити, брейк-данс, рэп, диджеинг, уличную моду, городское сленговое общение и социальный протест. Помимо этого, современные английские музыкальные термины тесно связаны с технологиями. Такие слова, как *remix*, *streaming*, *playlist*, *auto-tune*, стали неотъемлемой частью повседневной жизни, отражая глобальный и цифровой характер потребления и распространения музыки. В узбекском языке музыкальная терминология в большей степени связана с народными традициями, религиозными и историческими ценностями. Так, слово *maqom* несет глубокий духовный смысл. Это не только музыкальный жанр, но и понятие, отражающее терпение, внутреннее спокойствие и духовную чистоту. *Shashmaqom* — это музыкальное наследие узбекского и таджикского народов, вобравшее в себя множество религиозных и философских идей. Такие термины, как *ashula*, *yalla*, *lapar*, *navo*, связаны с устным народным творчеством. Эти песни исполняются во время свадеб, обрядов, хашаров и народных праздников, выражая коллективный дух узбекского народа, торжественность и радость. Также в последние годы в узбекский язык вошли музыкальные термины из английского, такие как *DJ*, *rap*, *remix* и другие. Однако они часто адаптируются под местный контекст. Например, выражения типа *gerchi bola* или *DJ Akmal* демонстрируют, как заимствованные термины осваиваются в народной речи. Это является ярким примером языкового взаимодействия между глобализмом и локальной культурой.

Язык и музыка — это два неразрывно связанных явления. Чувства, выраженные через музыку, часто оформляются именно через язык. Например, метафоры, рифмы и сленг, используемые в английских песнях, раскрывают культурный контекст. Особенно это заметно в *rap battles*, где язык используется как острое оружие, а каждое слово несет вес и значение. В узбекских народных песнях широко применяются архаические выражения, поэтические обороты и элементы фольклора. В частности, в жанре *o'lan* музыкальные выражения служат не только эстетическим целям, но и передаче духовного утешения, выражению скорби, памяти о покойных. Это усиливает социально-философскую нагрузку музыкальных терминов и форм.

Гендерный аспект также находит своё отражение в музыкальной терминологии. В английском языке термины *boy band* и *girl group* указывают не только на состав группы, но и на возраст, половые предпочтения аудитории, а также на содержание самой музыки. Такие группы часто формируются в рамках маркетинговых стратегий, что служит примером экономических и коммерческих коннотаций музыкальных терминов.

Вывод:

Проведённое исследование показало, что музыкальные термины в английском и узбекском языках не ограничиваются лишь лексическим значением, но также охватывают глубокие культурные и социальные пласты. В английском языке такие термины часто связаны с молодежными субкультурами, социальной идентификацией и политическим выражением. В узбекском языке музыкальная лексика, напротив, тесно связана с традиционными ценностями, духовностью и национальной историей. Различия в этих коннотациях обусловлены историко-культурным развитием двух народов, уровнем глобализации, а также ролью музыки в образовании и массовой культуре. Тем не менее, в современном глобальном пространстве английские музыкальные термины активно проникают в узбекский язык, особенно среди молодежи, способствуя формированию новых культурных пластов.

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HISTORICAL PROGRESS OF HYDRONYMS

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Abstract. Some toponymic research has been done on place names in Surkhandarya, although it is insufficient. Our scientists continue to ignore the research of other, microtoponyms, and particular hydronyms. The article also considers the microhydronyms in this area to do this. Focus on the history of hydronym research and the origins of hydronyms.

Keywords. Toponymy, hydronym, ethnic symbol, microhydronym, geographical terms, anthroponyms, geographical object, ethnographic, historical, microtoponym, rivers, lake, sea, stream, canal, armpit, strait, waterfall, names, oronymy, oikonymy, polynymy, springs, wells, ethnotoponyms, anthroponyms.

Annotatsiya. Surxondaryodagi joy nomlari bo'yicha ma'lum toponimik tadqiqotlar yetarli bo'lmas-da, olib borilgan. Olimlarimiz boshqa, mikrotoponimlar va alohida gidronimlarni o'rganishga e'tibor bermay kelmoqda. Maqolada buni amalga oshirish uchun ushbu sohadagi mikrogidronimlar ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Gidronimlarning tadqiqi tarixi va gidronimlarning kelib chiqishiga e'tibor qarating.

Kalit so'zlar. Toponimika, gidronim, etnik timsol, mikrogidronim, geografik atamalar, antroponimlar, geografik obyekt, etnografik, tarixiy, mikrotoponim, daryolar, ko'l, dengiz, soy, kanal, qo'litiq, bo'g'oz, sharshara, nomlar, oronimiya, oykonimiya, polinimiya, etnotoponimlar, quduqlar.

Аннотация. Некоторые топонимические исследования были проведены по топонимам Сурхандарьи, хотя их недостаточно. Наши ученые продолжают игнорировать исследования других, микротопонимов и отдельных гидронимов. В статье также рассматриваются микрогидронимы в этой области, чтобы сделать это. Сосредоточьтесь на истории исследования гидронимов и происхождении гидронимов.

Ключевые слова. Топонимия, гидроним, этнический символ, микрогидроним, географические термины, антропонимы, географический объект, этнографический, исторический, микротопоним, реки, озеро, море, ручей, канал, подмышка, пролив, водопад, названия, оронимия, ойконимия, полинимия, родники, колодцы, этнотопонимы, антропопонимы.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan has a small number of toponyms found in khorezmi, Sogdian, and old Turkic inscriptions. Our geographical names are likewise numbered, as they are described in Greek texts. Many of the oldest toponyms in literary sources for our region were documented between the end of the first millennium and the beginning of the second millennium. The books of the "Devoni lexicon-Turkish," "history of Bukhara," "territory ul-World," and "library of Arab geographers" are significant toponymic materials. The wind has not yet affected the form of the anchor of the geographical names listed in these monuments.

A person cannot function without a system of naming things. Everything in the

world has a name that helps to differentiate one item from another. People invented names to identify one area from another, one ravine from another, one street from another, the city and the villages. Geographic names, or toponyms, are examples of such names. The science of toponymy is concerned with toponyms. Toponymic consists of the Greek words topos –place and onoma (or onima)- name.

Toponymy is divided into several types. These are: gidronomy (Greek gidro-water), that is, the names of rivers, lakes, seas, shadows, channels, armpits, Straits, waterfalls; oronymy (Greek oros - mountain), that is, the names of the relief forms on the surface of the Earth-mountains, peaks, Heights, valleys, plains; oykonomy (Greek oykos - House), polynymia (Greek polis - city), that is, the names of villages and cities, microtoponymy (Greek micros - small), that is, small objects: springs, wells, fields, meadows, woodpeckers, gars, roads, bridges and even some tree names that have a horse with a horseshoe. In addition, toponyms with the names of different peoples, seeds-aymok are called ethnotoponyms (Grec Ethnos - folk). Toponyms, denoted by the names of people, are referred to as anthroponyms (Greek anthropos-man).

Gidronyms are also a kind of toponyms, they also have an important role in the language system.

It is necessary to consider the microgidronyms part of the toponyms and microgidronyms of the toponyms mentioned above. The study of gidronyms is of great importance for the history and theory of language. The scientist according to S. Qarayev, the professor of the Tomsk State Pedagogical Institute analyzing the kidronyms of A.P. Dulzon Siberia, he found that the territory where the people lived in ancient times was very wide. And now in Siberia, in particular on the banks of the River, there are about 500 people left in total. Toponymic data showed that at one time Kets were a very large number of people.

The most ancient information about Central Asia and its geographical names are three in the works of Greek scientists in the VI-V centuries BC. Herodotus Gercand (professional), known as the “father of historical science”, called the territory from the sea to the East “consisting of a vast plain”, spelled the Araks River (Amudarya). Then (the first century – The First Century) in the works of past Greek historians was called Oks (or Oksos). Scientists believe that these Oks (sometimes Acacia) are the origin of the ancient Turkish name of Amudarya – the word O'kuz “River”. In Avesto and other historical sources, the ancient names of Amudaryo called: Raha, Ranha, Aranha are also threeraydi. The Arabs called him Jaykhun "the river". There is also an opinion that jayhun called the Jewish Bible refers to the Jihondaryus, which is mentioned in the “Torah”, the peasant.

Information on the rivers, natural geography, cities of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, takes a definite shape when it comes to the first century.

Thus, in the works of scientists of the ancient world, many names were mentioned in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, the chunonchi Girkand sea, Araks (Amudarya), Oks (Oksos - Amudarya), Yaksart (the most ancient local name of Sirdarya), Politimet (Zarafshan) and others.

The geographical and toponymic heritage of Beruni is found in the works "At-tavkhim", "history of India", "Al-osorul Baqiya", "Qununi Ma'sudi". The scientist said that in Khorezm it was the name of malak, who controlled the waters of the Vakhsh, including the Jaykhun River. So, toponyms such as Vakhsh, Vakhshivar, Vakhshivordara, which is the right tributary of the Amudarya region, are a reflection of the name of that mermaid.

In the X century, the work "Kitab al-masolik and Al-mamolik" of Istarkhiy (Abu Iskhoq Ibrahim ibn Muhammad al-Farisiy) was the kata achievement of Arabic geography. Later, traveling to Movarounnahr, ibn Havqal, who described it, further supplemented his work Istarkhiy. For example, ibn Havkal testified that SAG'onrud (Chag'onrud), that is, was poured into the Amudarya below the city of Termez in Surkhandarya.

In addition to valuable information on history, ethnography, geography, there are also rich materials in the field of toponymy in the work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. The importance of "Bournemouth" in this bbora is that it is possible to learn from it ancient forms of toponyms: Saykhun, Khujand water or Secret water-Sirdarya, etc.k. Many geographical terms mentioned in Babur are of great importance in determining the origin of toponyms and in the development of scientific terminology in Uzbek, for example: hand-river network, hand-shadow with dry hand or without water, tagob - Ozen, obgir-swamp, obshor-waterfall and others.

A lot of materials on toponymic of Uzbekistan can be found from historical, linguistic and geographical works in the course of the next two centuries. One of the first works on the toponymic of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, is the work of the Hungarian scientist Armin Vamberi, which was the product of his secret trip to Central Asia, called "geographical names of Central Asia" (in German). In the dictionary part of the work, about 600 Geographical Names and terms are given in the composition of the alphabet. And this was a great achievement for that period.

More than a century and a half ago, the Russian linguist academician A.X. Vostokov paid attention to the fact that at the end of the names of the water bodies of Russia will come -ga, -ma, -ra, -ta, such joints will meet again and again.

A.X. Vostokov expressed the following opinion about the antiquity of the names. In any country, the names of rivers, lakes and natural geographic objects are more ancient than in the names of cities, countries, because before the cities were built many times, primitive people began to live in water bodies as a small group, and those who named these waters in their own language were the same in Russia. It will be in

several groups, depending on the similarity of the prefix or suffix of the Geographical Names. So, the scientist enters the group of Rivers Don, Dvina, Dunat, Dnepr, Dniester. Later, the scientist don so in the languages of the peoples who speak in the Iranian language Group. (According to A. Abayev, however, even in the current Ossetian language) it was determined that it means “river” (water).

Russian scientist A. Orlov also (1907) in his monograph titled “The origin of the names of some rivers, cities, tribes and places in Russia and Western Europe” (“Происхождение названий русских и некоторых западно-европейских рек, городов, племен и местностей”) there were several groups depending on the last suffixes in the names of rivers in the European part of Russia. Later, scientists compiled reverse dictionaries according to their last suffixes in order to determine the rows that end with such identical suffixes. Those began to think that such additives should have some kind of meaning and call them formant or topoformant.

The idea of the name of the city of Kazan is also worth noting. Rumor has it that the servants of The Botanist, when preparing food, dropped a pot into the water from the RAM, and since then this so-called pot. A.F. Orlov enumerates four shades called Kazan (Kazanka), and concludes that the city was even before the cheats for the arrival of the Mongols and, of course, was named after the Kazan River.

A.F.Orlov excessively overestimates the names of rivers and says that the peoples of the English, Bulvar, bur, german, German, Polish, Prussian are called Angel, Bur, Volga, Gera, Nemts, Poltsa, Russian rivers.

In Russia, it is permissible to briefly touch on the advantages of the method of studying Geographical Names by looking at the forms, especially on monographs.

As the author noted, they used the “list of rivers of the Dnieper Basin”, which was printed in 1913 year in St. Petersburg as the main source for this work. The book consists mainly of three parts the first upper Dnepr is devoted to the word-building types of Slavic gidronymia. The author divides the hydronymy of the upper Dnieper into 11 large types, depending on the suffixes. The next part from it is devoted to the etymology of kidronyms. On the basis of the gidronymia material, the division of the upper Dnieper necks into regions in terms of ethnicity and dialecticity forms the third part. The authors found that the Iranian elements meet in this region, especially in its South-East. Later this type of study of trubachev was devoted to the kidronyms of Ukraine on the Right Bank. In this game, along with the forms, a huge role was given to the forms of legalization of toponyms and the etymological analysis of the names of rivers.

V.A. Nikonov's "brief toponymic dictionary" ida tells about the history and origin of about 4 thousand toponyms in the former Union and foreign countries. The dictionary says that the name of the river Herirud in Afghanistan comes from the words Iranian harvaid – “succulent”, rud – “River” and E.M. Murzayev's etymology

"mountain river" is also cited.

V.V. Bartold believes that while this gidronym came from the name of the ancient Aryan tribe. Hence the initial name of herotus is Ari (heri). Herirud (Herotrud in some sources) is the river Aria, while Herot is threeraydi in the form of an Arabic plural.

"Territory ul-World" ("hadiths of the world") is a historical and geographical work written in the Persian language in 9898983 by an unknown author. In this game the names of the Movarounnahr Rivers mentioned. "The river jaykhun (Amu) flows through the Vahan region and flows through the Vahan region of the region of Bomir (Pamir) and Shignon and flows into the Khorezm sea." "The harnab (Panj) flows from the west of Qasark mountain and joins the Jayhun through Badakhshan and Polgar (Parxor)." "Another river, they call it Vakhshab, flows out of the Vakhsh mountains, flows into Jayhun near Vakhsh (city)." "Chaghanrud (Surkhandarya) flows from Chaghanion and is poured into Jaykhun near Termez." "Another one is Uzgand SUWU, which starts from the mountain of Khallukh (back) and passes by the cities of Uzgand, Bob (pup), Axsikat, Khujand, Banokat and reaches to the lands of Tu Choch, and then flows into the Khorezm sea." "Another river (now the ring River) is Khurshab, beginning from the outskirts of Buttamon, from the northern mountains and flowing into Uzganda (Sirdarya) near the city of Khurshab." "Another is that water is poured into its Ownganga". "Another river is Qubo (water), which is poured into Uzgand (water) near the city of Qubo." "Another is the Parak River, which passes through the choch lands, poured into the Uzganda. After all these rivers are added, the holistic water is called the Choch River, the Arabs (toziyon) call this river Saykhun" Parak is the Chirchik River.

In the work" territory " Zarafshan is called the Bukhara River. As can be seen from the same data, the rivers are often called by the names of cities and regions.

The author of "territory ul-World" called Sirdaryo Hasart in one place. Based on this, H. Hasanov draws such a conclusion: "it will be known that Sirdayo was named after Uzgand and Hasart on the soil of Uzbekistan in the X century. So, Harast is one of the local names, the Yaksart form, written in the books of the ancient Greeks, has changed from then on. Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far-an-Narshakhi (full name – Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far ibn Zakariyo ibn Hatab ibn Sharik), originally from the village of Narshakh in Bukhara, the history of Bukhara was written in Arabic in 943-944. Explanation of river names in the game. "There is a large river on the Samarkand side, which is called The River Rudi Mosaf – Mosaf" (This Is the River Zarashon).

The ancient Iranian name of amudarya was Wakhsh (Wakhshab). One of the largest tributaries of the river is now also called Vakhsh. Abu Rayhon Beruni Wahsh wrote that in the khorezms the name of the mermaid – pretty. According to professor H. Hasanov, in Pakistan Amudarya is now also called Vakshu-nada. In Central Asia,

there are several places called Vakhshivar, Vakhshivardara.

They say that the current name of the amudarya is derived from the name of the city (now the herder) of Amul (Omuy, Omuyya), which existed in the Middle Ages. It is also possible that the city received a name from the river. Academic V.V. Bartold's hypothesis that "this word must have come from the name of the amard people, even before the bees" goes forward. Mahmud Koshgariy mentioned that any quiet, stable, stagnant thing is called an Amule.

In historical sources, the names of the Termez River, Kalif River, Arang, Raha, Aranga, Urgench River, Khorezm River were found in Amudarya.

The etymology of the name of surkhandarya still remains a mystery. If the Tajik was in the meaning of "red water", it should have been called surkhob (the main part of the river – Denov to the name of the red water). There is also a Turkmen seed called Surx or surxi. In the Middle Ages, Amir was also called Chag'onrud in the history of Timur. V.V. Bartold said that in the Mongolian language chaghan is "white" (fasting is a river).

In 1926-th year V.B. Shostakovich's work "the historical ethnographic significance of the names of the rivers of Sibir" was printed. V.B. Shostakovich is also A.X. Vostokov and in the footsteps of O.F. Orlov there were 30 groups, depending on the similarity of the gidronyms in several river basins of Siberia. When he spoke about the Ob River, he concluded that the name of several rivers in Siberia ends with the suffix ob, which means that the Ob River has a name either "water" or "river". A.P. Dulzon found out that in Siberia there are more than 30 ob component gidronym.

It can be seen that in the territory of Surkhandarya, as in other places, the terms related to place names provide sufficient data for scientific analysis. It is known that science, which studies place names in science, is called toponymy, and the sum of Geographical Names is called toponymy. Toponymy is divided into several types. One of them is kidronimia, which refers to the names of rivers, lakes, seas, shades, gills, channels, armpits, Straits, springs, waterfalls. Gidronyms in the territory of surkhandarya have a number of peculiarities in connection with the history of the region, geographical conditions, features of the local people's language. Above, we briefly touched on the concept of gidronym and the history of its study. And the identification and collection of their linguistic formations is expressed in our further scientific work.

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“TARIXI ARBA’ ULUS” ASARIDA BADIY SAN’ATLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI

Malikova Zulayxo Baxromjon qizi
ToshDO‘TAU magistri

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Mirzo Ulug‘bekning “Tarixi arba’ ulus” asari haqida ma’lumotlar keltirilgan. Shuningdek, ushbu asarda badiiy tasvir vositalarining qo‘llanilishi ham qalamga olingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Mirzo Ulug‘bek, “Tarixi arba’ ulus”, badiiy tasvir vositalari, o‘xshatish, mubolag‘a, sifatlash, talmeh.

Аннотация: Аннотация: В статье представлена информация о произведении Мирзо Улугбека "Тарихи arba улус". Также рассматривается использование художественных образных средств в этом произведении.

Ключевые слова: Мирзо Улугбек, "Тарихи arba улус", художественные образные средства, аналогия, гипербола, характеристика, метафора.

Annotation: The article provides information about Mirzo Ulugh Beg's work "Tarixi arba ulus." Additionally, the use of artistic imagery techniques in this work is also discussed.

Keywords: Mirzo Ulugh Beg, "Tarixi arba' ulus," artistic imagery techniques, analogy, hyperbole, characterization, metaphor.

Mirzo Ulug‘bek - Temuriylar sulolasining eng mashhur vakillaridan biri bo‘lib, uning ota-bobolari o‘z zamonlarida buyuk hukmdorlar bo‘lishgan. Mirzo Ulug‘bek o‘z davrining odil podshohi bo‘libgina qolmay, balki zehni o‘tkir olim, zamonasining ilmfan yo‘lboshchisi, yorqin mayog‘i edi. Unda “ilm va podshohlikni barobar yuritgan hukmdor” timsolini ko‘rish mumkin. Chunki Mirzo Ulug‘bek hukmdorlik faoliyati bilan birga ilmiy faoliyatni ham teng olib borgan. Uning eng mashhur ishlari esa astronomiya sohasida bo‘lib, buning yorqin namunasi “Ulug‘bek rasadxonasi” hisoblanadi. Ushbu rasadxonada ko‘plab olimlar minglab yulduzlarning joylashuvini o‘rganganlar va turli astronomik jadvallar yaratganlar. Mirzo Ulug‘bek tarix, astronomiya, musiqa, she‘riyat, fizika, matematika, me‘morchilik bo‘yicha yetuk olim edi. O‘zi qurdirgan madrasalarda shaxsan o‘zi talabalar uchun ma’ruzalar o‘qigan, ilm ulashgan. Nafaqat madrasalar, balki maktablar, masjidlar, kutubxonalar, karvonsaroylar, ko‘priklar va bog‘lar qurilishi uchun ham homiylik qilgan.

Mirzo Ulug'bek faqat dunyoviy ilmlarnigina emas, balki diniy ilmlarni ham puxta egallagan podshoh edi. U yetti qiroat bilan Qur'oni karimni o'qiy oladigan inson edi. Bunday ilmni egallashida albatta ustozlarining o'rni alohida ahamiyat kasb etgan. Jumladan, Qozizoda Rumi, Jamshid al-Koshi, Ali Qushchi kabi ilmi va sadoqatli insonlarning saboqlari va yordamlarini ta'kidlab o'tish joiz.

Bugungi kungacha Mirzo Ulug'bek haqida ko'plab izlanishlar, tadqiqotlar olib borildi. Mirzo Ulug'bekning ilmiy merosini o'rganish XVII asrdan boshlangan. Bu borada Jon Grivs, Tomos Xayd, Frensis Beyli, L.Sediyo, V.Bartold, V.Vyatkin, E.Knobl, T.N.Qoriniyoziy, G'.Jalolov va boshqa olimlarning tadqiqotlarini ko'rsatish mumkin. Mazkur tadqiqotlarda Mirzo Ulug'bek ijodi, faoliyati turli nuqtayi nazardan o'rganildi¹¹. [1:274]. Xususan, O'zbekistonda ham Mirzo Ulug'bekka bag'ishlangan asarlar yaratildi. Masalan, M.Shayxzoda "Mirzo Ulug'bek" tragediyasi, X.Davron "Padarkush" she'ri, O.Yoqubovning "Ulug'bek xazinasi" kabi asarlar Mirzo Ulug'bekning shaxsiyatini ochib berish uchun muhim o'rin egalladi.

Shuningdek, Mirzo Ulug'bekning hayoti va faoliyatini har tomonlama o'rganish va ommalashtirish maqsadida 2024-yil 12-sentabrda "Buyuk qomusiy olim va mashhur davlat arbobi Mirzo Ulug'bek tavalludining 630 yilligini keng nishonlash to'g'risida" O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori ham e'lon qilindi va bu borada keng ko'lamli ishlar olib borildi. Ushbu qarorda "To'rt ulus tarixi" nomli tarixiy asarining o'zbek tiliga tarjimasini qayta nashr qilinishini qarorning bandiga kiritib o'tildi.

"Tarix-i arba ulus" ya'ni "To'rt ulus tarixi" Mirzo Ulug'bekning ilmiy rahbarligi va shaxsan ishtirokida yaratilgan. Asar 1425-yili yozib tamomlangan. Lekin Ovrupo sharqshunoslari orasida ushbu asarni birinchilar qatori o'rgangan va uning qisqartirilgan inglizcha tarjimasini e'lon qilgan polkovnik Mayls, yetarli asosi bo'lmagani holda bu kitobni "Shajarat ul-atrok" ("Turk (hoqon) larining shajarasi") deb ataydi.¹²

XVI asrning mashhur tarixchilaridan biri Mirzo Muhammad Haydar (1500-1551) ham Ulug'bekning tarix ilmi sohasida ham samarali mehnat qilganligini aytadi. Masalan, uning "Tarix-i Rashidiy" nomli yirik kitobida bu haqda mana bularni o'qiy: "Donishmand podshoh Mirzo Ulug'bek bir tarixiy asar yozdi va unga "Ulus-i arba" deb nom qo'ydi".¹³ Asarning to'liq nusxasi hozirga qadar topilmagan. Hozirgi kunda qisqartirilgan to'rt nusxasi saqlangan bo'lib, ikkitasi Angliyada, bir nusxasi Hindistonning Bankipur shahri kutubxonasida, to'rtinchi nusxasi AQShning Harvard universitetida saqlanib kelinmoqda. Asarda tarixiy shaxslar, tarixiy voqealar yoritib berilar ekan, albatta turli badiiy tasvir vositalaridan ham keng foydalangan.

¹¹ Abdullayeva M. Adabiy-tarixiy asarlarda kichik janrlar poetikasi. Doktorlik dissertatsiyasi. – Samarqand: 2021. – 274 b.

¹² The Shajarat ul-Atrak, or Geneological Tree of the Turks and tatars, trans and abrid. By Glonel Milles, London, 1832, b. 182^a

¹³ Tarix-i Rashidiy, O'zbekiston FA Sharqshunoslik instituti qo'lyozmasi, № 1430, v 85 a.

Xususan, metafora, jonlantirish, mubolag'a, metonimiya, sifatlash kabi badiiy san'atlarni ko'rishimiz mumkin. "Tarix-i arba ulus" asarida eng ko'p uchraydigan badiiy san'at bu- metafora hisoblanadi.

Metafora (yun. Metaphora- ko'chirish) – ma'no ko'chishining keng tarqalgan turlaridan biri, narsa-hodisalar orasidagi o'xshashlikka asoslanuvchi ko'chim turi, M. mohiyatan yashirin o'xshatish bo'lib, unda o'xshatilayotgan narsa tilga olinmagani holda, uning ma'nosini o'xshayotgan narsa (ya'ni uni ifodalayotgan so'z) bildiradi.¹⁴ Metaforada o'xshatilayotgan narsalar aynan o'xshash bo'lmasa ham, ularga xos belgilardan biri asos qilib olinadi. Va bu taqqoslash, qiyoslash matnning jozibadorligi va ta'sirchanligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Quyidagi misrada ijodkor oddiygina tish tasvirini "yuksak go'zallik timsoli" sifatida ifodalab bergan:

"Mehrim bilan yuzing quyoshini (nurga) to'ldirurman. Oynikidek la'l (tish) ingni dur qilurman"¹⁵. Birinchi misrada "yuzing quyoshi" iborasi orqali ma'shuqaning yuzi quyoshga o'xshatilib, tashbeh san'ati yuzaga kelgan. Oshiq mehri bilan yorning go'zal va nurafshon yuzini nurga to'ldirishni niyat qilgan. Ikkinchi misrada esa yorning tishi la'l- qimmatbaho va nodir toshdek ajoyibligiga urg'u berilyapti, hamda u oydek betakror va yagona. Shuningdek, tish oyning porloq va tiniqligiga o'xshatilyapti. Bu yerda mubolag'a san'atini ham ko'rish mumkin. "Mubolag'a (ar.- oshirish, orttirish) – mumtoz adabiyotdagi she'riy san'at, narsa-hodisalar, insonlar va boshqa mavjudotlarga xos xususiyatlarni tabiiy roliga nisbatan bo'rttirib, kattalashtirib yoki kichraytirib tasvirlash."¹⁶ Bu yerda shundoq ham la'ldek bo'lgan tishni endi dur-marvarid kabi qimmatbaho tosh qilishga rag'bat bildirilyapti. Bo'rttirish orqali tish yuqori baholanib, uning o'zgacha go'zalligi ochib berilyapti.

"Tarix-i arba ulus" asarida keltirilgan Qubilayxonning ta'rifi ham mubolag'a san'ati asosiga qurilgan: "Zimiston kechalari ulkan yog'ochlarni balandlatib yoqib qo'yib, yonida uxlar ekan. Agar o'sha otashdan uchqunlar, cho'g'lar sachrab yuziga kelib yopishadigan bo'lsa, xayolida pashsha chaqqandek bo'larkan. Goho o'zini kamtar tutib, uxlaganda yostiqday tosh qo'ygan". Bilamizki, haqiqatda olovning uchquni ham insonni zarar yetkazadi, tosh esa qattiq jism bo'lganligi sababli yostiq qilib uxlash mumkin emas. Ijodkor mubolag'a orqali obrazni aniqroq va ta'sirchanroq tasvirlashga erishgan.

Epitet (yun. Epitheton- ilova etilgan, izohlovchi)- badiiy sifatlash; narsa-hodisaning belgisini obrazli ifodalaydigan badiiy aniqlovchi.¹⁷ Epitet obyekt yoki shaxsga qo'shiladigan o'ziga xos sifat hisoblanadi, bu orqali shaxs yoki narsaning o'ziga xosligi yoritib beriladi. "Tarix-i arba ulus" asarida ham epitetlar ya'ni sifatlashlar ko'p bora qo'llanilgan. Masalan, "oltin uzuk", "temir darvoza", "g'isht

¹⁴ D.Quronov, Z.Mamajonov, M.Sheraliyeva- Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. T. "Akademnashr". 2013.

¹⁵ Mirzo Ulug'bek. "To'rt ulus tarixi". T. Yoshlar matbuoti. 55-bet.

¹⁶ D.Quronov, Z.Mamajonov, M.Sheraliyeva- Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. T. "Akademnashr". 2013.

¹⁷ D.Quronov, Z.Mamajonov, M.Sheraliyeva- Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. T. "Akademnashr". 2013.

devor” kabi sifatlashlarni asarni mutolaa qilish davomida uchratish mumkin.

“Tarix-i arba ulus” asarida talmeh san'atidan ham unumli foydalanilgan. “Talmeh (ar. – chaqmoq chaqishi, ko'z qirini tashlash, nazar solmoq) – mumtoz adabiyotdagi she'riy san'at, she'rda mashhur tarixiy voqea, shaxslar, badiiy asarlarga ishora qilish”.¹⁸ Ushbu asarda ko'plab tarixiy voqealar, tarixiy shaxslar haqida ma'lumotlar bor. Xususan, Chingizxon, Shohrux Mirzo, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Amir Temur, Abdurazzoq Samarqandiy, Mahmud Torobiy kabi mashhur tarixiy shaxslarning faoliyati keng yoritib berilgan. Masalan, “Sohibqironi a'zam Chingizxoni muazzamning lashkari behisob edi, ular soatma-soat ko'payib borishardi va goh-goh kurash maydonini sulton Jaloliddin uchun tang qilar edilar”.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, “Tarix-i arba ulus” asarida tarixiy ma'lumotlar turli badiiy san'atlar vositasida ifodalanganligi, asarning qiymatini yanada oshirishga xizmat qilgan. Asarda Chingizxon va uning avlodlari haqida mufassal ma'lumotlar keltirilganligi esa tarixiy manba sifatida muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligidan dalolatdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Abdullayeva M. Adabiy-tarixiy asarlarda kichik janrlar poetikasi. Doktorlik dissertatsiyasi. – Samarqand: 2021. – 274 b.
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5. Tarix-i Rashidiy, O'zbekiston FA Sharqshunoslik instituti qo'lyozmasi, № 1430, v 85 a

¹⁸ D.Quronov, Z.Mamajonov, M.Sheraliyeva- Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. T. “Akademnashr”. 2013.

LANGUAGE AS A MEANS OF SHAPING NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Annotation. Language plays a central role in the construction and preservation of national identity. It acts not only as a communication tool but also as a cultural symbol that unites people through shared heritage, values, and worldview. This paper explores how language contributes to national identity formation by analyzing theoretical frameworks, sociolinguistic practices, and historical examples. The study demonstrates that language serves both as a marker of belonging and a means of national consciousness reinforcement.

KEY WORDS: national identity, language, cultural heritage, linguistic nationalism, sociolinguistics, identity formation.

Аннотация. Язык играет центральную роль в построении и сохранении национальной идентичности. Он действует не только как инструмент коммуникации, но и как культурный символ, объединяющий людей через общее наследие, ценности и мировоззрение. В этой статье рассматривается, как язык способствует формированию национальной идентичности, путем анализа теоретических основ, социолингвистических практик и исторических примеров. Исследование показывает, что язык служит как маркером принадлежности, так и средством укрепления национального сознания.

Ключевое слова: Национальная идентичность, язык, культурное наследие, лингвистический национализм, социолингвистика, формирование идентичности.

Annotatsiya. Til milliy o'zlikni shakllantirish va saqlashda markaziy rol o'ynaydi. U nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki umumiy meros, qadriyatlar va dunyoqarash orqali odamlarni birlashtiruvchi madaniy timsol sifatida ham ishlaydi. Ushbu maqola nazariy asoslar, sotsiolingvistik amaliyot va tarixiy misollarni tahlil qilish orqali tilning milliy o'zlikni shakllantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, til ham mansublik belgisi, ham milliy ongni mustahkamlash vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy o'ziga xoslik, til, madaniy meros, lingvistik millatchilik, sotsiolingvistika, o'zlikni shakllantirish.

National identity is a multifaceted and intricate concept that is frequently impacted by politics, language, culture, and history. Language is unusual among these in that it can be used both practically and symbolically. A nation's cultural memory, customs, and beliefs are ingrained in its language, which also makes interpersonal communication easier. This study looks at how language shapes and maintains national identity, especially in post-colonial and multilingual cultures where linguistic politics frequently reflect battles for cultural sovereignty.

How Our Identity Is Shaped by Language: Appreciating the Influence of...
Both our sense of self and our group identity are influenced by language. Our thoughts,

perceptions, and even emotional responses are influenced by the language or languages we use. The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis states that a language's structure affects how its speakers understand and interpret the outside world.

Language is a symbol of cultural distinctiveness and more than just a system of signs. It spreads traditional knowledge, customs, and folklore. Many communities, particularly those who are indigenous or marginalized, view language preservation as an integral part of maintaining their cultural identity. For example, initiatives to revive the Welsh and Maori languages are nationalistic endeavors that seek to regain cultural sovereignty in addition to being linguistic endeavors.

Language policies are frequently used by governments as instruments of nation-building. Many nations institutionalize a national language after gaining independence in an effort to bring their different populations together. For instance, in order to maintain interethnic harmony and fortify national identity, Kazakhstan has promoted Kazakh in addition to Russian. On the other hand, as demonstrated in Sri Lanka and Ukraine, stringent language laws have the potential to isolate linguistic minority and ignite societal instability.

Language may bring people together and drive them apart in multilingual society. By attempting to strike a balance between English and French-speaking identities, Canada's bilingual policy promotes inclusivity. Multilingualism, however, also makes it difficult to forge a unified identity. It takes inclusive language planning that upholds minority languages and fosters common national values to navigate such diversity.

Language-based national narratives can be effectively spread through the mass media and educational institutions. How citizens view themselves is influenced by the language used for instruction and the way historical events are framed. In post-colonial African nations, for example, media and textbooks frequently serve two purposes: they promote official languages and preserve indigenous languages to foster unity and international engagement.

Scholars such as Benedict Anderson (1983) emphasized the role of language in creating "imagined communities," where shared language helps construct a sense of collective belonging. Joshua Fishman (1999) and Edward Sapir (1921) contributed foundational theories linking language and cultural identity. The research methodology employed in this paper is qualitative and comparative, analyzing existing literature, historical case studies, and sociolinguistic data from countries such as France, Kazakhstan, and Canada. This interdisciplinary approach enables a nuanced understanding of the dynamic between language policies and national identity formation.

It is crucial to stress that social activity is carried out by people, not by languages or hypothetical institutions like states. The majority of social actors are

forced to employ language in their efforts to achieve goals in the world. However, as they do so, they are interacting with the accessible language resources or accessing. They encounter these resources in both helpful and restricting ways as a result of this engagement. As a result, we draw the conclusion that it is critical to consider the ways in which access to cultural and linguistic resources is organized, first due to the profound social differences among speakers of the same language and, second, because English is a dominant global language in the modern world.

Therefore, the allocation of access to linguistic resources is a political matter rather than one pertaining to the nature of knowledge or language. This affects how social researchers study important issues related to languages and social identities as well as how policymakers address them. We support a different methodological starting point, one that views the study of language use as a properly sociolinguistic exercise, namely that social action determines language use, as opposed to beginning with the assertion that there are distinct languages and then going on to study, for instance, their correlation with certain ethnic or national forms of identification, or how and in what ways they have become impure or hybridized.

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The Power of Body Language in International Communication

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Annotation: This paper explores the significance of body language in international communication. It examines how non-verbal cues such as gestures, facial expressions, and posture affect interaction between individuals from various cultures. The objective of this paper is to demonstrate that communication is not solely based on verbal language but is also heavily influenced by body language. The analysis includes real-life examples to highlight the topic.

Keywords: Body language, non-verbal communication, cross-cultural interaction, gestures, diplomacy.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola xalqaro muloqotda tana tilining ahamiyatini o'rganadi. U imo-ishoralar, yuz ifodalari kabi og'zaki bo'lmagan belgilar turli madaniyatlarga mansub shaxslar o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlarga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi muloqot nafaqat og'zaki tilga asoslanganligini, balki tana tilidan ham kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatishini ko'rsatishdir. Tahlil mavzuni yoritish uchun hayotiy misollarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tana tili, og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot, madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sir, imo-ishoralar, diplomatiya.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается значение языка тела в международном общении. В ней рассматривается, как невербальные подсказки, такие как жесты, выражения лица и поза, влияют на взаимодействие между людьми из разных культур. Цель этой статьи — продемонстрировать, что общение основано не только на вербальном языке, но и на него сильно влияет язык тела. Анализ включает примеры из реальной жизни, чтобы подчеркнуть эту тему.

Ключевые слова: Язык тела, невербальное общение, межкультурное взаимодействие, жесты, дипломатия.

Introduction.

In today's interconnected world, communication goes far beyond words. One of the most powerful yet often overlooked aspects of interaction is body language — the unspoken signals we send and receive through our physical behavior. From a simple smile to a firm handshake, these non-verbal cues play a vital role in how messages are interpreted and relationships are built. This is especially important in international contexts, where gestures can carry different meanings across cultures. Understanding and mastering body language is not only useful in everyday communication but is also essential in diplomacy and international relations, where subtle cues can influence the outcome of negotiations and strengthen global partnerships. This chapter explores the significance of body language in communication and highlights its crucial role in international affairs.

Chapter 1: Understanding Body Language in Communication

Body language is a non-verbal form of communication where physical behaviors are used to convey messages. These behaviors include facial expressions, gestures, posture, eye contact, and personal space. Body language is often unconscious but plays a significant role in how we interpret each other's intentions and emotions. For instance, a simple smile can indicate warmth, while crossed arms might signal defensiveness or disagreement. Eye contact can suggest confidence, but in certain cultures, it may be perceived as disrespectful. In international communication, it is essential to understand the meaning of body language as it can have different interpretations across cultures. A gesture that signifies approval in one country may be offensive in another. Therefore, understanding these differences can help prevent communication breakdowns. Professionals working in international contexts must not only be fluent in verbal communication but also in reading and using body language appropriately. In conclusion, body language is a powerful tool in communication,

especially in international settings. Mastering body language can improve interactions and foster better understanding among people from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Chapter 2: Body Language in Diplomacy and International Relations

In diplomacy and international relations, body language plays a crucial role in establishing trust and facilitating communication between people from different countries. Diplomats frequently engage in discussions and negotiations where both verbal and non-verbal signals are important. Body language can influence the course of these interactions in meaningful ways. For instance, gestures such as maintaining open body posture or making direct eye contact can convey attentiveness and openness, which are essential in diplomatic discussions. Conversely, non-verbal signs like avoiding eye contact or displaying a closed posture can imply distrust or disinterest. These subtle cues can directly affect the outcomes of negotiations, meetings, and diplomatic agreements. Moreover, in diplomatic contexts, cultural sensitivity is critical. Certain gestures, such as a handshake or a bow, are considered appropriate in some cultures but may be misunderstood or even considered disrespectful in others. Therefore, diplomats are trained not only in linguistic skills but also in understanding and utilizing body language to ensure successful communication in various cultural contexts. In summary, body language serves as a powerful tool for diplomats and international communicators. By mastering this form of non-verbal communication, individuals can enhance their interactions, build stronger relationships, and navigate cultural differences more effectively.

Conclusion

To conclude, body language plays an undeniable role in the success of communication, particularly in international relations. While words are vital, non-verbal cues can express more than what is said and often convey emotions and intentions more strongly. For diplomats and international professionals, being aware of body language and understanding cultural differences is crucial to fostering better communication and avoiding miscommunication. As the world continues to grow more interconnected, the significance of body language in international interactions will only increase, making it a vital aspect of diplomatic work and cross-cultural communication.

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Ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi maqollarning lisoniy olami

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi maqollarning sintaktik- qiyosiy tahlili amalga oshirilgan bo'lib, tahlil natijalariga ko'ra ular o'rtasida o'xshash va farqli holatlar aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: paremiologiya, qiyosiy tahlillar, o'ziga xoslik, fe'lli iboralar.

Аннотация. В статье проводится синтаксическо-сопоставительный анализ пословиц на английском, немецком и узбекском языках, по результатам анализа выявлены сходства и различия между ними.

Ключивые слова: паремиология, сопоставительный анализ, особенность, глагольные фразы.

Abstract. The article contains a syntactic-comparative analysis of proverbs in English, German and Uzbek languages, and the results of the analysis reveal similarities and differences between them.

Key words: paremiology, comparative analyses, peculiarity, verbal phrases.

Jahon tilshunosligida maqollarni to'plash va ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini tadqiq qilish bo'yicha sezilarli ishlar amalga oshirildi. Xususan, jahon tilshunosligida V.Mider, N.Norrik, P.P.Grizbek va bir qancha boshqa paremiologlar¹⁹ ushbu sohada ilmiy tadqiqot olib borishgan. Shuningek, V.Mider, M.Kusi, V.Dal, G.Permyakov, J.Spik, J.Simpson, O.Lauhakzngas va yana bir necha olimlar²⁰ turli tillardagi

¹⁹ Mieder W. Origin of proverbs. In: Gotthard H.H., Varga M.A. (ed.) Introduction to paremiology: A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies.-Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open,2014.-p.28-44; Norrick N.R. Subject Area, Terminology, Proverb Definitions, Proverb Features. In Gotthard H.H., Varga M.A.(ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: Comprehensive Guide to Proverb studies.-Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open,2014.p7-27; Grzybek P. Semiotic and semantic aspects of the Proverb. In Gotthard H.H., Varga M.A.(ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: Comprehensive Guide to Proverb studies.-Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open,2014.p68-108; Jensesek V. Pragmatic and Stylistic Aspects of Proverbs. In Gotthard H.H.,Varga M.A.(ed.) Introduction to Paremiology: Comprehensive Guide to Proverb studies.-Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open,2014.p133-161;Прекина Н.В. Градуальная семантика русских пословиц.Автореф.дисс.канд.филол.наук.-М.,2005.-с22.

²⁰ Mieder W., Kingsbury S.A. and Harder K.B. A Dictionary of American proverbs.-N.Y.:Oxford University press, 1992.-p728; Kuusi M. Towards an International Type –system of Proverbs. – Heksinki: Academia Scientiarum Fennica, 1972. – p221; Даль В.И. Пословицы русского народа.(издание третье) – М.:Товарищество М.О.Вольф, 1904.-с.1096;Permyakov G.L. From Proverb to Folk-Tale. Notes on the general theory of Cliche. –М.: Nauka,1979.-p.286; Speake J., Simpson J. The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs. Fifth edition. – N.Y.:Oxford University Press,2008.-p625; Lauhakangas O. Categorization of Proverbs. In Gotthard H.H,Varga M.A.(ed.) Introduction to

maqollarning tasnifini yaratishdi va huning asosida paremiologik lug'atlar tuzishdi. O'zbek olimlari Sh.Rahmatulayev, O. Madayev, Z.Masharipova, A.Mamatov, O'.Yusupov ishlarida²¹ maqol hamda uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari borasida atroflicha to'xtalib o'tilgan bo'lsa, H.Berdiyev va R.Rasulov, Sh..Shomaqsudov va Sh.Shorahmedov, T.Mirzayev, A.Musoqulov va B.Sarimsoqov, K.Karamatova va H. Karamatovlar tomonidan yaratilgan lug'atlar²² o'zbek maqolshunosligining rivojida katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu olimlar yaratgan bunday ilmiy asarlar dunyo tilshunosligida ham paremiologiya sohasida chog'ishtirma metodda amalga oshirilgan ko'pgina ilmiy tadqiqotlarda asosiy manba sifatida, shuningdek, o'zbek tilini o'rganayotgan xorijiy fuqarolar u olganligi asarlarning qanchalik keng ko'lamli foydalanuvchilarga ega ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

Maqollarning sintaktik strukturasi (tuzilishi) ot, sifat, fe'l va ko'p hollarda qofiya, ritm va alleteratsiya (bir xil yoki ohangdosh undoshlarning qaytarilishi, yonma — yon kelishi) kabi til birliklaridan tashkil topishi mumkin.

M: *Viel lachen, viel geläutet. (Nemis)*

Tit for tat. (Ingliz)

O'z uying – o'lan to'shaging. (O'zbek)

Biz qiyosiy tahlilni amalga oshirayotgan tillardagi maqollarda sintaktik struktura asosan ot kesimli gaplar va sodda yig'iq va sodda yoyiq gaplar singari katta guruhlarda bo'lingan holda tadqiq qilinadi.

Ingliz va nemis tillarida ot kesimli gap shaklidagi maqollar asosan to be va sein fe'llari bilan ifodalanib kelingan bo'lib, o'zbek tilida bu shakl asosan kesim vazifasini bajaruvchi ot so'z turkumi bilan yoki fe'lning noaniq shakli – infinitiv bilan ifodalanadi:

Habit is second nature.

Gewohnheit wird zur zweiten Natur.

Odat – ikkinchi tabiat.

Ingliz va nemis tilidagi ayrim maqollar ot-kesim shaklidagi gaplarda asosan sifatning qiyosiy darajasi ishtirokida shakllanib, bu holatni biz ayrim o'zbek tilidagi

Paremiology: Comprehensive Guide to Proverb studies.-Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open,2014.p49-66.

²¹ Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек фразеологиясининг асосой маъно турлари. –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 2007.-Б.115; Маматов А.Э. Ўзбек тили фразеологизмларининг шаклланиш масалалари. Филол.фан.докт....дисс.-Т.,1999.-Б.317;Юсупов Ў.Қ. Contrastive Linguistics of the English and Uzbek languages/Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларининг чоғиштирма лингвистикаси. Т.:Академнашр,2013.-Б.262.

²² Бердиёров Х, Расулов Р. Ўзбек тилининг паремиологик луғати. (Университетлар ва педагогика институтларининг филология факультетлари студентлари учун қўлланма). –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1984.-Б.288;Шомақсудов Ш, Шораҳмедов Ш. Ўзбек мақолларининг изоҳли луғати. Нега шундай деймиз.-Т:Ғафур Ғулом, 1988. Б286; Мирзаев Т., Мусоқулов А. Ва Саримсоқов Б. Ўзбек халқ мақоллари.Т:Шарқ,2005.-Б.257; Караматова К.М.,Караматов Х.С. Proverbs. Мақоллар.Пословицы.-Т.Меҳнат,2000.-Б.398.

maqollarida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

A false friend is worse than open enemies.

Ehrlicher Feind ist besser als falscher Freund.

Yolg'on do'stdan ochiq dushman yaxshi.

Quyida biz qiyoslab o'rganayotgan maqollarda esa ot-kesim bilan sifatning orttirma darajasi ham shakllantirilganligini ko'rish mumkin:

Experience is the best teacher.

Erfahrung ist der beste Lehrmeister.

Tajriba – yaxshi ustoz.

Biroq ko'p miqdordagi uch tilda ifodalangan maqollarda asosan ot so'z turkumida ifodalangan kesim shakli ifodalanadi:

Time is money.

Zeit ist Geld.

Vaqt – pul.

Ba'zi maqollarda ot –kesim shakli qo'shma gaplarda ham ishtirok etib, bu holatni uch tildagi maqollarda ham kuzatish mumkin:

Speech is silver, but sielence is gold.

Reden ist Silber, Schwegen ist Gold.

Gapirganing kumush, gapirmaganing oltin.

Ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi ayrim maqollar ritmik holatni saqlab qolish uchun to'liqsiz gap ko'rinishida o'z ifodasini topadi, ya'ni ularda gapning markazi hisoblangan kesimning tushib qolishi mumkin:

Out of the rain into the eaves.

Vom Regen in die Traufe kommen.

O'tdan qochib yashinga tutilmoq,

Yom'irdan qochib do'lga.

Ingliz va nemis tillaridagi maqollarining ayrimlarida ot-kesim to be – sein fe'llarisiz, faqat ohang va yordamchi tinish belgilari yordamida ifodalanadi:

No pain, no gain.

Ohne Fleiß, kein Preis.

Mehnatsiz rohat yo'q.

Chog'ishtirilayotgan uch tildagi maqollarda ayrim hollarda ot-kesim egasi noma'lum gap shaklida o'z ifodasini topadi:

Better your own bread than another's roast.

Besser eigenes Brot als fremder Braten.

(Begona qovurdoqdan o'zingni noning yaxshiroq.)

O'zganing oshidan o'zingning qattiq noning afzal.

Ayrim maqollar ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillarida buyruq mayli mazmunidagi gaplardan iborat bo'lib, ular asosan pand-nasihat mazmunini ifodalaydi.

Live and learn.

Man lernt, solange man lebt.

(Ko'p o'qisang- ko'p yashaysan.)

Beshikdan to qabrgacha ilm izla.

Ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi maqollarning strukturaviy-qiyosiy tahlilini amalga oshirish davomida yana bir katta guruh tasnifiga murojaat qilamiz, ya'ni sintaktik jihatdan maqollar sodda yig'iq va sodda yoyiq gaplar ko'rinishida bo'ladi.

Biroq biz tahlilni amalga oshirayotgan tillardagi maqollar bir ma'no-mazmun ifodalasa-da, sintaktik strukturasi bir biridan farqlanishi kabi holatlar ham tadqiqot davomida kuzatiladi.

One scabbed sheep will mar a whole flock.

Ein räudiges Schaf steckt die ganze Herde an.

Bitta tirraqi buzoq butun podani bulg'aydi.

Tahlil qilinayotgan tillardagi ba'zi maqollar tarkibida ishlatilayotgan fe'llar va yordamchi fe'llar soniga ko'ra bir biridan farqlanishi mumkin:

A barking dog seldom bites.

Hunde, die viel bellen, beißen nicht.

Ko'p xurgan it tishlamas.

Qiyoslanayotgan tillardagi ayrim maqollarda uch tillarda ham gap qurilishidagi butunlay katta farq ko'rinishi mumkinki, ularni faqat umumiy bir mavzu o'zaro birlashtirib tura oladi:

You can't eat your cake and have it.

Hin is thin, verlohen ist verlohen.

(Yo'qolgani yo'qoladi, ichidagi qolaveradi.)

Yo'qolganing topilmaydi.

O'tgan ishga o'kinma.

Ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi ayrim maqollarda shakl qisman bir biriga o'xshash bo'lib, faqat ular tarkibida qo'llanilgan zamon shakli o'zaro farqlanib turadi:

A steady drop will carve the stone.

Steter Tropfen höhlt den Stein.

(Kuchli tomchi toshni o'yadi.)

Tomchi toshni kesar.

Chog'ishtirilayotgan uch tillarda maqollarning ayrimlari nafaqat gap tuzilishiga ko'ra, balki ularda zamonlarning qo'llanilishi bilan ham bir biriga mutanosiblikni ko'rsatadi:

After rain comes sunshine.

Nach Regen kommt Sonnenscheinen.

(Yomg'irdan keyin quyosh charaqlaydi.)

Oyning o'n beshi qorong'u bo'lsa o'n beshi yorug' bo'ladi.

Ingliz va nemis tillarida ayrim maqollarda ishlatiladigan modallik ma'nosini ifodalaydigan fe'llarda moslik o'zbek tillaridagi maqollar mazmunida ham ifodalanishi mumkin:

A man cannot do more than he can.
Über deinen Schatten kannst du nicht springen.
 (Soyangdan sakrab o'tib ketolmaysan)

Bo'yingni yetmagan joyga cho'zma.

Ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi maqollar sodda yig'iq gap yohud soda yoyiq gaplarda ifodalanganda, shakl jihatdan uch tilda katta tafovutni ko'rish mumkin:

Nothing stings like the truth.
Wahrheit tut der Zunge weh.
 (Haqiqat og'izni og'ritadi.)

To'g'ri so'zning to'qmog'i bor.

Ayrim maqollarda ingliz va nemis tillarida shakl jihatdan mavjud bo'lgan farqlar o'zbek tilidagi maqollarda ham butunlay boshqa holat va mazmunda kuzatilishi mumkin:

Who has the choice, has the suffering.
Wer die Wahl hat, hat die Qual.
 (Istak bo'lsa barcha imkoniyatlar ochiladi.)
Bildim tutildim, bilmadim qutuldim.

Ayrim maqollar ingliz tilida shart ergash gapli qo'shma gaplar orqali ma'lum bir ma'no-mazmun ifodalab keladi, biroq biz qiyoslab tahlil qilayotgan boshqa tillarda bu mazmun oddiy qo'shma gaplar yoki ega yashiringan gap ko'rinishida aks etadi:

If time comes, advice comes.
Kommt Zeit, kommt Rat.
 (Vaqtlar keladi, maslahatlar keladi.)
Omon bo'lsak ko'rarmiz.

Ingliz va nemis tillarida o'zbek maqoliga shaklan emas, balki mazmunan muqobil bo'la olishi mumkin bo'lgan maqol borligi ko'zga tashlanadi.

Masalan: *Every country has its own customs.*

Jedes Land hat seine eigenen Gebräuche.

Agar bu maqolni so'zma-so'z tarjima qiladigan bo'lsak, quyidagicha ma'no kelib chiqadi: «Har bir davlatning o'z odati bor». O'zbek tilidagi muqobili esa: «Har gulning o'z isi bor, har elning o'z tusi bor». Bu maqollar ma'no jihatidan bir-biriga mos kelishiga qaramasdan, sintaktik tahlil jarayonida ingliz va nemis tillaridagi maqol sodda gap shaklida, o'zbek tilidagi muqobili esa, teng bog'langan qo'shma gap ekanligini kuzatishimiz mumkin.

Ingliz va nemis tillarida o'zbek maqoliga shaklan yoki mazmunan to'g'ri keladigan maqol bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan: *The lion is not so fierce as he is painted.*

Löwe ist nicht so wild, wie er gemalt wird.

Ushbu maqolning o'zbek tilidagi tarjimasida quyidagicha: «Sher rasmidagidek qo'rqinchli emas». Uning o'zbek tilidagi muqobil varianti esa: «Qo'rqoqqa qo'sh ko'rinar». Yuqorida keltirgan maqollarni tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak, ularning semantik va sintaktik jihatdan mutanosib ekanini sezishimiz mumkin.

Out of the rain into the eaves.

Vom Regen in die Traufe kommen.

O'tdan qochib yashinga tutilmoq,

Yomg'irdan qochib do'lga.

Ushbu maqol biz qiyoslayotgan tillarda turli strukturaviy ko'rinishida tahlil qilinadi. Masalan, ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi variantlarida u ma'lum ma'noga ega barqaror birikma ko'rinishida ifodalansa, uning nemis tilidagi ekvivalentida u tugallangan ma'no va shaklga ega sodda gap bo'lib qo'llaniladi.

Wealth is nothing without health.

Gesunder Mann, Reicher Mann.

Sog'lik – tuman boylik.

Sog'lik inson hayotidagi eng muhim omil mazmunidagi bu maqolda esa nemis tilidagi ifodasi biz tahlil qilayotgan qolgan tillardan farqli ravishda ma'noviy birikma ko'rinishida, ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ot kesimli sodda gap ko'rinishida o'z ifodasini topgan.

Tit for Tat.

Ein finster Blick kommt finster zurück.

(Qanday qarash bo'lsa shunday javob qaytadi.)

Salomga yarasha alik.

Asosiy manba sifatida foydalanayotgan adabiyotlarda ayrim maqollarning variantlari bir-biriga aynan to'g'ri kelmaydi. Shuning uchun ham, maqollarning sintaktik jihatlarini chuqur o'rganish va ularni sintaktik tahlil qilish orqali ingliz, nemis va o'zbek tillaridagi ekvivalentlarni to'g'ri tanlay olamiz.

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TIL VA MANTIQ UYG'UNLIGI: TA'LIM JARAYONIDA TAFAKKURNI SHAKLLANTIRISH MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til va mantiq uyg'unligining falsafiy va kognitiv asoslari hamda ta'lim jarayonida tafakkur shakllanishi masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, til va mantiq uyg'unligiga oid nazariyalar ta'lim jarayonida tafakkur rivoji uchun qanday pedagogik yondashuvlar zarurligini ochib beradi. Maqola til va tafakkur bog'liqligini tushunishga oid nazariylarni taqdim etib, zamonaviy ta'lim amaliyotida tafakkurni shakllantirish bo'yicha muhim tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: til, tafakkur, mantiq, til falsafasi, kognitiv psixologiya, ta'lim, tafakkur shakllantirish.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются философские и когнитивные основания единства языка и логики, а также вопросы формирования мышления в образовательном процессе. Отмечаются образовательные выводы: как понимание языковых закономерностей и логического мышления влияет на развитие познавательных умений учащихся. Статья представляет теоретические концепции единства языка и логики и выдвигает рекомендации для современного педагогического процесса.

Ключевые слова: язык, мышление, логика, философия языка, когнитивная психология, образование, формирование мышления.

Annotation: This article explores the philosophical and cognitive foundations of the unity between language and logic, and issues of forming thought in education. The implications for education are discussed, showing how language structure and logical reasoning underpin students' cognitive development. The article presents theoretical conceptions of language-logic unity and offers pedagogical recommendations for developing critical thinking in learners.

Keywords: language, thought, logic, philosophy of language, cognitive psychology, education, cognitive development.

Zamonaviy ta'limning asosiy talablari orasida o'quvchining mustaqil fikrlashi, tahlil qilishi, muammoga yechim topa olishi va fikrini mantiqan asoslab ifoda eta bilishi birinchi o'rinda turadi. Til bu yerda nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki ongni shakllantiruvchi asosiy omil sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, til ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda mantiqiy tafakkurning o'rni beqiyosdir. Maktab bosqichida bu ikki jarayon – ya'ni til o'rgatish va tafakkur tarbiyasi – integratsiyalashgan holda olib borilsa, o'quvchining nafaqat til, balki umumiy tafakkur

madaniyati shakllanadi. Zamonaviy ta’lim paradigmasi bilim berishdan ko‘ra, fikrlashni o‘rgatish, axborotni tahlil qilish, sabab-oqibat munosabatlarini tushunish, tanqidiy yondashuv va asosli mulohaza yuritish kabi kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishga qaratilgan. Bu esa ta’limda til va mantiqiy tafakkur o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikka e’tiborni kuchaytirishni taqozo etadi. Til o‘rgatish, ayniqsa ona tili fanining o‘zagi – faqat grammatik normalarni emas, balki fikrni ifodalash, asoslash va tahlil qilishga xizmat qilishi zarur. Chunki til – bu fikrlashning, mantiqning tashqi shaklidir. Aynan shuning uchun mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish orqali til ko‘nikmalarini takomillashtirish nafaqat lingvodidaktik, balki falsafiy, psixologik va mantiqiy yondashuvni ham talab etadigan dolzarb ilmiy muammodir.

XX-XXI asrlarda til-tafakkur uyg‘unligi masalasiga kognitiv psixologiya ham yondoshuv kiritdi. Masalan, so‘nggi tadqiqotlar til strukturalari ongni shakllantirishini qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi. Tilga oid biologik va madaniy omillar tafakkur yechilishida o‘ynaydigan rolni ko‘rsatdi: so‘z boyligi va grammatik qulaylik tushunchalarni o‘zlashtirish jarayonini tezlashtiradi, fikrni samaraliroq ifodalashga yordam beradi. Til va mantiqning neyrobiologik aloqasi ham aniqlanishda; ichki nutq va diqqat, xotira jarayonlari ko‘p hollarda bir tizimda faoliyat yuritadi. Shu bilan birga, Humboldtning ilgari surgan g‘oyasi – har bir til odamga turlicha dunyoqarashni beradi – kognitiv lingvistika tomonidan qayta qo‘llab-quvvatlanmoqda. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlar til va fikrlashning uzviy bog‘liqligini tasdiqlayapti, bu esa mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish uchun til omillarini hisobga olish zarurligini anglatadi.

Til va mantiq uyg‘unligi nazariyalari zamonaviy ta’limda muhim axborot beradi. Bilim va tushunchalar hosil bo‘lishi dastlab ijtimoiy muloqotda sodir bo‘ladi. Xususan, murabbiy darsda muammolarni yechishda savol-javob, guruh muhokamalari va debatlardan foydalansa, talabaning mantiqiy tafakkuri mustahkamlanadi. Masalan, Vygotskiy yuqori aqliy jarayonlar – masalan, mantiqiy mulohaza va tushuncha shakllantirish – avval boshqalarning yordami bilan paydo bo‘lib, keyin shaxsiy tafakkurda mustahkamlanishi mumkinligini ko‘rsatgan. Ta’lim metodlarida tilga alohida e’tibor qaratish ayniqsa muhim: grammatikani chuqur tushuntirish, mavzuga doir atamalarni aniqlik kiritish orqali o‘quvchilarning fikr doirasi kengaytiriladi. Shuningdek, o‘quvchida ichki nutq (ichki suhbat) faoliyatini rag‘batlantirish ham muhim – masalan, tayyorlovchi topshiriqlarni birinchi bo‘lib og‘zaki ifodalaydigan talaba keyinchalik xotirasida shu fikrlash tarzini mustaqil tarzda takrorlaydi. Amaliy jihatdan, pedagoglar mantiqiy fikrlash va abstrakt tushunchalar ishlab chiqilishi uchun interfaol o‘qitish strategiyalarini qo‘llashi lozim. Masalan, matematikada so‘zlardagi muammolarni yechish jarayonida ham til elementlaridan foydalaniladi: auditoriyaga ma’lum atamalar berib, talabalarga masala mazmunini tushunishga yordam berish mumkin. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, o‘qituvchilar o‘quvchilarning “mantiq va mulohaza kabi asosiy kognitiv ko‘nikmalarini” rivojlantirishga ko‘proq

e'tibor qaratishi lozim. Shuning uchun ham fanlararo integratsiya (masalan, matematikani hikoya qilish bilan o'rganish, ilmiy-ommabop matnlarni tahlil qilish) o'quvchilar tafakkurini kengaytiradi. Boshqacha aytganda, til va mantiqqa oid nazariy izlanishlar pedagoglarga ta'limda muntazam muhokama, munozara va tahlil usullarini ko'proq qo'llashga asos beradi.

Til o'rganishda mantiqiy tafakkurni shakllantirish quyidagi elementlar orqali amalga oshiriladi:

1. Sabab-oqibatli bog'lanishlarni anglash (Masalan, "Nega bu fikr noto'g'ri bo'lishi mumkin?");
2. Taqqoslash va qarama-qarshi fikrlarni solishtirish;
3. Dalillash va xulosalash ("Sizning fikringizga qanday dalil bor?");
4. Tahlil asosida mulohaza yuritish (Matnni qismlarga ajratish, asosiy g'oyani aniqlash);
5. Nutqiy izchillik (Fikrni mantiqan bog'lab bayon etish).

Til ko'nikmalarining mukammalligi faqat grammatik bilim bilan emas, balki mantiqiy tafakkur bilan uyg'unlashgan holda rivojlanadi. Bugungi maktab ta'limi bu ikki elementni integratsiyalash orqali o'quvchining nutqiy va tafakkuriy salohiyatini oshirish imkoniga ega. Mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish esa o'quvchining tilni chuqur anglashini, tahlil qilishini, izchil va asosli fikr yuritishini ta'minlaydi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, til va mantiq uyg'unligi nazariy konsepsiyasi tilshunoslik, psixologiya va falsafa yutuqlarini yagona konseptda jamlaydi. Til tafakkurning shakllanishi va mantiqiy fikrlashni kuchaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shu sababli zamonaviy pedagogika til va mantiqiy muloqot imkoniyatlaridan faol foydalanib, talabalarda mavhum fikrlash va tahliliy tafakkurni mustahkamlashga urinish kerak. Tavsiya etilgan nazariy yondashuvlar dars jarayonini yanada boyitishi, o'quvchilar tafakkurini sistematik ravishda rivojlantirishga xizmat qilishi mumkin.

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Language and Identity: How Dialects and Accents Shape Cultural Belonging

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola til va madaniy identifikatsiya o'rtasidagi murakkab aloqani, xususan sheva va lahjalarning insonning o'zini biror guruhga mansub deb his etishida qanday rol o'ynashini o'rganadi. Ijtimoiy tilshunoslik nazariyalari, amaliy holatlar va madaniyatlararo misollar asosida tilning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy identitetni shakllantirishdagi o'rni yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: til, identitet, sheva, lahja, sosiolingvistika, madaniy mansublik, mintaqaviy tafovut.

Аннотация

Статья исследует сложные отношения между языком и культурной идентичностью, особенно как диалекты и акценты формируют чувство принадлежности. На основе социолингвистических теорий, практических кейсов и межкультурных примеров анализируется роль языка в построении и выражении идентичности.

Ключевые слова: язык, идентичность, диалект, акцент, социолингвистика, культурная принадлежность, региональные различия.

Abstract

This article explores the intricate relationship between language, particularly dialects and accents, and the formation of cultural identity. It investigates how linguistic variation contributes to one's sense of belonging, social categorization, and group affiliation. By analyzing sociolinguistic theories, case studies, and cross-cultural examples, the article offers a comprehensive look at the role of language in constructing and negotiating identity in diverse communities.

Keywords: language, identity, dialect, accent, sociolinguistics, cultural belonging, regional variation.

1. Introduction

Language is more than a tool for communication; it is a fundamental aspect of identity. The ways we speak—our choice of words, pronunciation, and rhythm—signal who we are, where we come from, and often how others perceive us. Dialects and accents are particularly salient features of language that can affirm group membership or trigger exclusion. In the age of globalization, the intersection between language and identity has become increasingly complex, involving issues of nationalism, migration, social stratification, and cultural pride.

This article focuses on how dialects and accents serve as linguistic markers of cultural belonging and personal identity. We begin with theoretical frameworks from sociolinguistics and anthropology and move on to practical examples illustrating how these linguistic variations operate in real-world contexts.

2. Theoretical Framework

Sociolinguistics offers valuable insights into the function of dialects and accents. Labov (1972) argues that language variation is deeply rooted in social structure and reflects patterns of inequality, power, and solidarity. According to Giles and Coupland (1991), the theory of communication accommodation suggests that speakers adjust their linguistic behavior to converge with or diverge from others,

signaling affiliation or distinction.

Furthermore, Bourdieu's (1991) notion of linguistic capital emphasizes how certain dialects and accents are socially valued over others, affecting speakers' access to resources, opportunities, and status. In multilingual societies, accent and dialect become powerful indicators of regional loyalty, ethnicity, and even resistance to dominant ideologies.

3. Dialects and Regional Identity

Dialects, defined as regionally distinct varieties of a language, often carry strong cultural significance. In the United Kingdom, for instance, regional dialects such as Scouse (Liverpool), Geordie (Newcastle), and Cockney (London) are closely tied to local identity. People take pride in their dialects, which serve as symbols of heritage and community.

Similarly, in the United States, Southern American English or African American Vernacular English (AAVE) are more than just linguistic codes—they are expressions of shared history, resistance, and solidarity. Speakers of AAVE, for example, navigate complex social dynamics, balancing between authenticity within their community and the pressures of assimilation in mainstream institutions.

In Italy, the use of regional dialects like Neapolitan or Sicilian highlights deep-rooted cultural divisions and contributes to strong regional identities, often superseding national identity. These dialects are passed down through generations and maintain unique phonological and lexical features distinct from Standard Italian.

4. Accents and Social Perception

Accents, unlike dialects, are primarily concerned with pronunciation. Yet, they too are powerful indicators of social belonging and are often loaded with judgments. Sociolinguistic research shows that people make assumptions about intelligence, trustworthiness, and socio-economic status based solely on accent.

For instance, speakers with Received Pronunciation (RP) in the UK are often perceived as educated and authoritative, whereas those with Birmingham or Glaswegian accents may face negative stereotypes. In the U.S., a Midwestern accent is often considered "neutral" or "standard," which has implications for employment, particularly in media and broadcasting.

Accents can also signal ethnicity and migration. Immigrants are frequently judged based on their non-native accents, which may become a barrier to social integration or professional advancement. However, some communities embrace their accented English as a badge of cultural identity, turning a perceived deficit into a marker of pride.

5. Language, Identity, and Discrimination

Linguistic discrimination, or "linguicism," is a form of bias wherein individuals are treated differently based on their language use. This can occur in educational

settings, the workplace, or in legal systems. For example, students who speak in non-standard dialects may be unfairly evaluated or underestimated in academic contexts.

In the labor market, accent discrimination persists despite legal protections. Job applicants may be rejected due to perceptions of their accent being "difficult to understand" or "unprofessional." These biases can marginalize speakers and limit their access to economic mobility.

Legal battles in countries like the U.S., UK, and Canada have attempted to address linguistic discrimination, but enforcement remains inconsistent. Nevertheless, awareness of this issue has grown, and many organizations now promote linguistic diversity as part of their inclusion policies.

6. Globalization and Hybrid Identities

In an increasingly interconnected world, linguistic identities are becoming more fluid. Diaspora communities, for example, often develop hybrid linguistic practices, combining features of their heritage language with the dominant language of their host country. This results in new dialects and accents that reflect complex, layered identities.

Youth language in global cities like London, New York, and Toronto exemplifies this hybridity. Multicultural London English (MLE), for instance, blends elements of Caribbean, South Asian, and West African Englishes with traditional Cockney, creating a new dialect that reflects the city's diversity.

Technology and social media also influence linguistic identity. Platforms like TikTok and YouTube provide spaces where non-standard accents and dialects gain visibility and even popularity. These platforms challenge traditional hierarchies and offer alternative narratives about who gets to be heard and respected.

7. Preservation and Revitalization

Efforts to preserve endangered dialects and minority languages have gained momentum globally. Communities are increasingly recognizing the importance of linguistic heritage in maintaining cultural identity. In places like Wales, Ireland, and the Basque Country, language revitalization programs have led to increased usage of native dialects.

In the U.S., initiatives to support Native American languages aim to reclaim cultural knowledge lost through colonization. Similarly, in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, the revalorization of local dialects and accents forms part of a broader cultural renaissance.

Language activists argue that dialect and accent preservation is not about resisting change, but about maintaining diversity and honoring the linguistic richness of human expression.

8. Conclusion

Dialects and accents are far more than linguistic curiosities—they are central

to how individuals and communities define themselves. They serve as audible symbols of cultural belonging, heritage, and identity. However, they also function within systems of power, where some ways of speaking are privileged over others.

Understanding the sociolinguistic dimensions of dialect and accent helps reveal broader patterns of inclusion, exclusion, pride, and prejudice. As societies become more diverse and multilingual, fostering respect for linguistic variation becomes essential for social cohesion and cultural sustainability.

To celebrate dialects and accents is to recognize the full spectrum of human voice and experience. Rather than erasing differences in the pursuit of uniformity, we must listen to the multitude of ways in which identity is expressed through language.

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FUNCTIONS OF PERSONAL NAMES IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Annotation

This article explores the functions of personal names in English literary texts. The author analyzes how names function not only as identifiers but also as tools for characterization, ideological framing, cultural referencing, intertextual allusion, and emotional or stylistic enhancement. Drawing on examples from different genres and periods, the paper highlights the semantic and symbolic load carried by anthroponyms in shaping narrative meaning.

Keywords: personal name, literary character, linguoculture, intertextuality, naming, symbolism.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz adabiy matnlarida shaxs ismlarining funksiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Muallif personaj ismlarining nafaqat identifikatsiya vositasi, balki badiiy xarakter yaratish, ideologik yondashuvni ifodalash, madaniy va intertekstual ishoralar berish, emotsional fon yaratishdagi o'zni haqida misollar asosida fikr yuritadi. Turli davr va janrlardagi ingliz adabiyotidan olingan namunalarda shaxs ismiga yuklangan semantik va stilistik yuklamalar ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxs ismi, adabiy personaj, lingvokultura, intertekst, obraz, badiiy ism.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются функции личных имен в английских литературных произведениях. Автор анализирует, как имена используются не только для идентификации персонажей, но и как средства характеристики, выражения идеологических взглядов, культурных аллюзий, интертекстуальных связей и создания эмоционального или стилистического эффекта. Примеры из английской литературы разных эпох демонстрируют семантическую и символическую нагрузку, которую несут антропонимы.

Ключевые слова: личное имя, литературный персонаж, лингвокультура, интертекстуальность, именованье, символика.

In literary texts, **personal names** are central to meaning-making. As the most common type of proper name, anthroponyms (names of people) serve not only to identify characters but also to suggest psychological depth, social background, symbolic roles, and narrative functions. They often carry **semantic, cultural, and emotional weight** beyond their surface function. According to Van Langendonck and Van de Velde (2016), personal names possess a hybrid linguistic status—they are partly referential and partly expressive, shaped by cultural context. This paper investigates the key literary functions of anthroponyms and illustrates them through examples from English-language literature.

In literary texts, the functions of anthroponyms can range from supporting character development to conveying ideological and symbolic meanings. The most common functions of personal names in literature include the following:

- Identification and differentiation;
- Characterization and symbolism;
- Cultural and ideological function;
- Narrative and structural function;
- Intertextual and allusive function;
- Emotional and stylistic function.

The most basic function of a personal name in literature is to **distinguish characters** from one another. In narrative fiction, a name allows readers to track character development and participate in the fictional world. For instance, in George Orwell's *1984*, names like "Winston Smith" sound intentionally generic, emphasizing the erasure of individuality in a totalitarian society. As Leech and Short (2007) note, even in their simplest form, names influence reader expectations: a name like "Ebenezer Scrooge" carries archaic and harsh phonetic features that match his stern, miserly nature in Dickens's *A Christmas Carol*.

Personal names often serve to **express character traits**, social roles, or fate. In some cases, names are **descriptive** or allegorical. For instance, in John Bunyan's *The Pilgrim's Progress*, characters like "Christian," "Hopeful," and "Ignorance" reflect moral or spiritual states. Similarly, in *The Importance of Being Earnest* by Oscar

Wilde, the name “Ernest” symbolizes honesty, and the pun on the word becomes central to the play’s satire on identity and social norms. As Algeo (1985) explains, symbolic naming can either **reinforce a reader’s perception** or **ironically contrast** with a character’s behavior, adding complexity to the narrative.

Anthroponyms also reflect **cultural background, ethnic identity, and social ideology**. In postcolonial and diaspora literature, personal names are often markers of resistance and self-definition. For example, in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s *Americanah*, the protagonist Ifemelu’s name remains unaltered in the U.S., symbolizing her commitment to her Nigerian identity. The refusal to “Westernize” her name becomes a narrative act of cultural preservation. Ngugi wa Thiong’o (1986) emphasizes that colonialism sought to replace native personal names with Anglicized versions as a means of **ideological domination**. Reclaiming traditional names in literature is thus both a political and literary gesture.

Personal names can function as **plot devices**. Sometimes, they contain clues, references, or ironies that foreshadow events or reveal hidden connections. In Shakespeare’s *Romeo and Juliet*, the family names “Montague” and “Capulet” are symbolic of inherited conflict. Juliet’s famous line - “What’s in a name? That which we call a rose by any other name would smell as sweet” - questions whether love can transcend identity and societal labels (Shakespeare, 1597/2004). In mystery or detective fiction, names are sometimes selected to mislead or create narrative tension. A name might carry false associations, or echo someone from the past, contributing to the story’s suspense.

Writers often name characters after **historical, religious, or literary figures** to signal parallels or contrasts. These anthroponyms act as **intertextual devices**. In James Joyce’s *Ulysses*, the character Stephen Dedalus draws on the myth of Daedalus from Greek mythology, suggesting themes of creativity, entrapment, and escape. These connections deepen the reader’s understanding through **cultural memory** (Bakhtin, 1981). In contemporary literature, this function may also involve parody. For instance, in dystopian works, using classical or biblical names can create **ironic distance** between the reader’s expectations and the world depicted.

Personal names can also evoke **emotion**, contribute to the **tone**, or provide **stylistic texture** to a literary work. Names may carry phonetic qualities - euphony or cacophony - that match a character’s temperament. In J.K. Rowling’s *Harry Potter* series, names such as “Severus Snape” use sharp, sibilant sounds to suggest coldness and ambiguity. Meanwhile, “Albus Dumbledore” evokes gentleness and whimsy. In comic literature, unusual or exaggerated names are used for humorous or satirical purposes. P.G. Wodehouse invents names like “Gussie Fink-Nottle” to entertain and characterize at once.

Conclusion

Personal names in literary texts are deeply **functional**, not merely decorative. They serve as tools for identification, characterization, cultural expression, narrative structure, and emotional resonance. Whether symbolic, ideological, or aesthetic, anthroponyms reflect both the inner world of characters and the broader cultural and literary contexts in which they are embedded. Understanding how personal names function in fiction enhances both stylistic analysis and cultural interpretation. As anthroponyms continue to evolve in literature, they remain one of the most potent devices for expressing identity, meaning, and memory.

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THE ROLE OF PRAGMATICS IN CROSS- CULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

Pragmatics, the study of how language is used in context, plays a vital role in cross-cultural communication. While grammar and vocabulary enable basic understanding, pragmatic competence ensures that language is used appropriately according to cultural norms. Differences in politeness strategies, speech acts, indirectness, and turn-taking often lead to misunderstandings between speakers of different cultural backgrounds, even when they share a common language. This paper explores how such pragmatic differences can result in communication breakdowns, particularly in intercultural interactions involving greetings, requests, refusals, or expressions of disagreement. Real-world examples illustrate how cultural expectations shape linguistic behavior. The paper also emphasizes the importance of teaching pragmatic awareness in language education to prepare learners for authentic communication. By highlighting the intersection of language, culture, and social context, this study argues for greater attention to pragmatics as a key factor in fostering effective and respectful cross-cultural dialogue.

Key words: pragmatics, cross-cultural communication, politeness strategies, speech acts, indirectness, language competence, intercultural misunderstanding, language teaching.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Прагматика, наука о том, как язык используется в контексте, играет важную роль в межкультурной коммуникации. Хотя знание грамматики и словарного запаса обеспечивает базовое понимание, именно прагматическая компетенция позволяет использовать язык уместно в соответствии с культурными нормами. Различия в стратегиях вежливости, речевых актах, степени косвенности и правилах ведения диалога часто приводят к недоразумениям между представителями разных культур, даже если они говорят на одном языке. В данной работе рассматриваются примеры таких различий и их влияние на общение, особенно в ситуациях приветствия, просьб, отказов и выражения несогласия. Особое внимание уделяется необходимости преподавания прагматических навыков в процессе изучения иностранных языков. Исследование подчеркивает важность прагматики как ключевого элемента эффективного и уважительного общения между культурами.

Ключевые слова: прагматика, межкультурная коммуникация, стратегии вежливости, речевые акты, косвенность, языковая компетенция, межкультурные недоразумения, преподавание языка.

Annotatsiya:

Tilning kontekstda qanday qo'llanilishini o'rganuvchi soha - pragmatika - madaniyatlararo

muloqotda muhim o'rin tutadi. Grammatik va lug'aviy bilimlar asosiy tushunishni ta'minlasa-da, aynan pragmatik kompetensiya tilni ijtimoiy va madaniy me'yorlarga mos tarzda ishlatishni ta'minlaydi. Turli madaniyatlardagi odoblilik strategiyalari, so'z axtarlari, bilvosita ifoda va navbat almashinuvi kabi farqlar, hatto bir tilning o'zida ham, muloqotda noto'g'ri tushunishlarga olib kelishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi bunday pragmatik tafovutlar tahlil qilinadi, xususan, salomlashish, iltimos qilish, rad etish va e'tiroz bildirish kabi holatlardagi muammolar ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola, shuningdek, chet tilini o'rganishda pragmatik ongni rivojlantirish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqot til, madaniyat va ijtimoiy kontekstning uzviy bog'liqligini yoritib, pragmatikani samarali va hurmatli muloqotning muhim omili sifatida ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmatika, madaniyatlararo muloqot, odoblilik strategiyalari, so'z axtarlari, bilvosita ifoda, til kompetensiyasi, madaniyatlararo tushunmovchilik, til o'qitish.

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly interconnected and multicultural world, effective communication across languages and cultures has become a vital skill. While mastering grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation is often emphasized in second language learning, one critical component is frequently overlooked: pragmatics. Pragmatics is the study of how language is used in context, including the influence of social norms, cultural expectations, and situational factors on communication. Language is not only a system of words and rules—it is also a tool for building relationships, expressing politeness, managing conflict, and conveying subtle social meanings. In cross-cultural communication, even fluent speakers can experience misunderstandings if they lack pragmatic competence. For example, what is considered polite in one culture might be perceived as distant or even rude in another. Such misinterpretations often stem from differences in speech acts, indirectness, politeness strategies, and norms for turn-taking. This paper explores the crucial role of pragmatics in cross-cultural interactions, highlighting how pragmatic differences influence communication outcomes. It also examines real-life examples of pragmatic failure and discusses how raising awareness of these differences can lead to more respectful and effective intercultural dialogue. By understanding and teaching pragmatics, language learners and professionals alike can navigate cultural diversity with greater sensitivity and success.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a qualitative research design, as it seeks to explore the complex, context-dependent nature of pragmatic use in cross-cultural communication. A qualitative approach allows for a deep, interpretive understanding of how individuals from different cultural backgrounds use language in social interactions and how pragmatic failures or mismatches occur. Rather than relying on numerical data, this research emphasizes meaning, experience, and interpretation. The primary data sources for this study include recorded real-life conversations between speakers from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds, classroom interactions among language learners, and written reflections or anecdotal reports of communication breakdowns caused by

pragmatic misunderstandings. Additionally, examples from textbooks and language teaching materials were analyzed to assess how pragmatic features are introduced and taught in language education contexts. To guide the analysis, this study draws on several theoretical frameworks: Speech Act Theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969), Politeness Theory (Brown & Levinson, 1987), and Intercultural Pragmatics (Kecskes, 2014). These theories provide a foundation for identifying and interpreting pragmatic elements such as requests, refusals, greetings, indirectness, turn-taking, and expressions of disagreement across different cultural norms. Discourse analysis was employed as the main analytical method. Each interaction was examined in terms of context, speaker intent, cultural background, and the pragmatic strategies used. Special attention was given to how and why misunderstandings occurred, and what cultural or linguistic factors may have contributed. The findings aim to identify recurring patterns that illustrate both successful and failed intercultural communication, with the goal of emphasizing the need for pragmatic awareness in language education and international settings. By using this methodology, the study not only highlights the challenges faced by language learners and native speakers in intercultural environments but also provides pedagogical insights into how pragmatic competence can be improved through explicit instruction and cultural sensitivity training.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal several recurring patterns of pragmatic failure in cross-cultural communication, primarily rooted in differences in politeness norms, indirectness, and context-sensitive language use. One of the most common issues identified was the misinterpretation of speech acts, such as requests or refusals. For instance, learners from high-context cultures often expected more indirect forms of communication and perceived direct statements as rude or overly blunt. Conversely, speakers from low-context cultures sometimes viewed indirect expressions as vague or evasive. Another key observation was the variation in politeness strategies. In some cultures, it is customary to use hedging and softening phrases to maintain harmony and avoid confrontation, whereas in others, clarity and efficiency are prioritized. These differing approaches led to misunderstandings, especially in professional or academic settings where cooperation depends heavily on mutual understanding and respect. Turn-taking norms also posed challenges. In certain cultures, interrupting is seen as a sign of engagement and enthusiasm, while in others it is considered impolite. Such mismatches in expectations often led to participants feeling ignored or disrespected, even when no offense was intended. Furthermore, pragmatic failures were not only seen among language learners but also among fluent speakers who lacked cultural awareness. This demonstrates that grammatical accuracy alone is not enough to ensure successful communication. Without pragmatic competence, even well-constructed sentences can lead to breakdowns in interaction. The discussion also highlights the

importance of teaching pragmatics explicitly in language education. Many textbooks focus on grammar and vocabulary while ignoring culturally appropriate language use. Incorporating real-life dialogue examples, role-plays, and reflective activities on cultural norms can significantly improve learners' ability to navigate cross-cultural situations. Overall, the results emphasize that effective communication requires not just linguistic skills, but also cultural sensitivity and pragmatic awareness. Bridging these gaps can foster more meaningful, respectful, and productive interactions across languages and cultures.

CONCLUSION

In an era of globalization, the ability to communicate effectively across cultures is more important than ever. This study has demonstrated that pragmatic competence plays a critical role in cross-cultural communication, often determining whether an interaction results in understanding or misunderstanding. The findings reveal that pragmatic failures—such as misinterpreted speech acts, conflicting politeness norms, and differing turn-taking conventions—can occur even among fluent speakers if cultural awareness is lacking. It is clear that linguistic proficiency alone is insufficient for successful communication in multicultural contexts. Language learners must also develop the ability to interpret and use language appropriately within different cultural frameworks. This calls for a greater emphasis on pragmatics in language education, including the explicit teaching of culturally sensitive communication strategies. By fostering pragmatic awareness, educators and learners can help bridge the gap between linguistic ability and cultural understanding. This not only enhances mutual respect and collaboration but also contributes to more meaningful and effective global interaction.

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“O'TGAN KUNLAR” va “ANDISHA VA G'URUR” ASARLARIDA MILLIY QAHRAMONLARNI YARATISHDAGI IJODKOR MAHORATI

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Annotatsiya

Milliy qahramonlar tushunchasi asrlar davomida tarixiy rivoyatlarda, adabiyot va san'atda markaziy mavzu bo'lib kelgan. Bu raqamlar ko'pincha jamiyatning ideallari, fazilatlari va intilishlarini ifodalaydi. Bu qahramonlarni yaratishdagi ijodiy va badiiy mahorat, xususan, oldingi tarixiy davrlarga oid asarlar o'sha davrning ijtimoiy-siyosiy, madaniy va hissiy manzaralari haqida ko'p narsalarni ochib beradi. O'tgan asrlardagi asarlar, xoh ular adabiy matnlar, badiiy asarlar, ilmiy kashfiyotlar yoki falsafiy risolalar bo'lsin, zamonaviy madaniyat, tafakkur va taraqqiyotni shakllantirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynadi. Ko'pincha "madaniy meros"ning bir qismi deb ataladigan bu asarlar nafaqat o'z davrining intellektual yutuqlarini ifodalaydi, balki kelajakdagi rivojlanish uchun asosiy qurilish bloklari bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ushbu maqolada “o'tgan kunlar” asarlarida milliy qahramonlar yaratilishi ortidagi badiiy jarayon va madaniy kontekst o'rganilib, ular adabiyot, tasviriy san'at va spektakl orqali qanday tasvirlanganligi o'rganiladi. Bu siymolar ortidagi ijodiy mexanizmlarni chuqur o'rganish orqali ularning milliy o'ziga xoslik va jamoaviy xotiraga ta'sirini yaxshiroq tushunishimiz mumkin. Ushbu maqola "o'tgan kunlar" asarlarining doimiy ahamiyatini o'rganadi, ularning madaniy o'ziga xoslikni saqlash, inson bilimni oshirish va intellektual nutqni rivojlantirishdagi rolini tahlil qiladi. Maqolada o'tmishdagi asarlar merosi bugungi kunni anglash va kelajakni shakllantirish, inson tabiati, jamiyat taraqqiyoti va ilmiy kashfiyotlar haqida muhim tushunchalar berishda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kashfiyot, madaniyat, ijtimoiy-siyosiy, milliy qahramon, intellektual, hissiy, adabiyot, ta'sir, muhim.

Аннотация

Концепция национальных героев была центральной темой в исторических повествованиях, литературе и искусстве на протяжении столетий. Эти фигуры часто представляют идеалы, добродетели и стремления общества. Творческие и художественные навыки, задействованные в создании этих героев, особенно в работах более ранних исторических периодов, многое раскрывают о социально-политических, культурных и эмоциональных ландшафтах того времени. Работы прошлых веков, будь то литературные тексты, произведения искусства, научные открытия или философские трактаты, сыграли ключевую роль в формировании современной культуры, мысли и прогресса. Эти работы, часто называемые частью «культурного наследия», представляют собой не только интеллектуальные достижения своего времени, но и служат фундаментальными строительными блоками для будущих разработок. В этой статье исследуется художественный процесс и культурный контекст, лежащие в основе создания национальных героев в работах «давно минувших дней», исследуя, как они изображались в литературе, изобразительном

искусстве и перформансе. Углубляясь в творческие механизмы, стоящие за этими фигурами, мы можем лучше понять их влияние на национальную идентичность и коллективную память. В этой статье исследуется непреходящая важность произведений «из далекого прошлого», анализируется их роль в сохранении культурной идентичности, развитии человеческих знаний и развитии интеллектуального дискурса. В статье утверждается, что наследие прошлых произведений имеет решающее значение для понимания настоящего и формирования будущего, предоставляя существенные знания о природе человека, развитии общества и научных открытиях.

Ключевые слова: открытие, культура, социально-политический, национальный герой, интеллектуальный, эмоциональный, литература.

Annotatsiya

The concept of national heroes has been a central theme in historical narratives, literature, and art for centuries. These figures often represent the ideals, virtues, and aspirations of a society. The creative and artistic skills involved in crafting these heroes, particularly in works from earlier historical periods, reveal much about the socio-political, cultural, and emotional landscapes of the time. Works from past centuries, whether they be literary texts, artworks, scientific discoveries, or philosophical treatises, have played a pivotal role in shaping contemporary culture, thought, and progress. These works, often referred to as part of the "cultural heritage," represent not only the intellectual achievements of their time but also serve as fundamental building blocks for future developments. This article explores the artistic process and cultural context behind the creation of national heroes in works of the "days gone by," examining how they were portrayed through literature, visual arts, and performance. By delving into the creative mechanisms behind these figures, we can better understand their impact on national identity and collective memory. This article investigates the enduring importance of works from "days gone by," analyzing their role in preserving cultural identity, advancing human knowledge, and fostering intellectual discourse. The article argues that the legacies of past works are critical for understanding the present and shaping the future, providing essential insights into human nature, societal development, and scientific discovery.

Key words: discovery, culture, socio-political, national hero, intellectual, emotional, literature, impact, essential.

KIRISH

Mustaqillik davrida ingliz va o'zbek adabiyotining rivojlanishida xorijiy davlatlar bilan ilmiy adabiy aloqalar kuchayib bormoqda. Ayniqsa, millatimizni jahon miqyosiga olib chiqayotkan milliy asarlarni yaratgan ijodkorlarni ijodini tipalogik usulda o'rganish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Jahon adabiyotining ta'siri o'zbek adabiyotining shakllanishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Dunyo adabiyotshunosligda milliy qahramonni yaratishda ijodkor badiiy mahorati muammosi ingliz adiblarining asarlarida aks etgan o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, ularning ijtimoiy belgilari asosida tasniflanishi kabi masalalar ustida tadqiqotlar olib borilayotgan bo'lishiga qaramasdan ijodkor badiiy mahorati muammosini keng qamrovda o'rganish ta'qozo etmoqda. Ingliz romantizmning yetuk mutafakkuri Jane Austen asarlarida milliy qahramon yaratish mahorati turli aspektlarda talqin etilgan. Mana shuning uchun bir ijodkorning o'zidan keying adiblar va boshqa milliy adabiyotlarga ta'sirini o'rganish ta'qozo etadi. Shuning uchun ingliz romantizm bilan o'zbek jadid adabiy vakillarini qiyoslab

o'rganish oldimizga qo'yilgan maqsadga olib kelishi mumkin.

O'zbek adabiyotshunosligining milliy adabiyoti taraqqiyotida muhim ro'l kashf etgan Abdulla Qodiriy jahon adabiyotidagi asosiy tendensiyalardan xabardor bo'lgan. Bu jihatdan ingliz-o'zbek adabiy aloqalari va XX asr boshlarida milliy adabiyotlarda sodir bo'lgan ijodiy jarayonlarni qiyosiy o'rganish maqsadga olib kelishi mumkin. Negaki, "adabiyot- jamiyat hayotida ezgu qadriyat va an'analarni chuqur qaror toptirishda, xususan, xalqimiz, ayniqsa yosh avlodning ma'naviy-intelektual salohiyati, ongu tafakkuri va dunyo qarashini yuksaltirishda, ona-Vatani va xalqiga muhabbat hamda sadoqat tuyg'usi bilan yashaydigan barkamol shaxsni tarbiyalashda beqiyos ahamiyatga ega" yangi bosqichida milliy adabiyotshunosligimizda falsafiy fundamental asarlarni, ulardagi obrazlar va xronotopni jahon Renessansi davri ijod namunalari, ensiklopedik xarakterga ega bo'lgan shoh asarlar bilan tipologik tadqiq etish ustuvor vazifalar qatoriga kiradi.

ASOSIY QISM

Abdulla Qodiriy "O'tkan kunlar" romanida milliy qahramonlarni yaratishda o'zining badiiy mahoratini namoyon etadi. U xalqning urf-odatlarini, an'analari va tarixiy voqealarini chuqur tahlil qilib, qahramonlar orqali milliy ruhni aks ettiradi.

Milliy qahramonlar va ularning tasvirlanish.

Otabek roman davomida adolat va erkinlik uchun kurashadi. U o'zining qishloqdagi adolatsizliklarga qarshi chiqishi, o'z xalqining haq-huquqlarini himoya qilishga intilishi bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, Otabekning o'z qishlog'ida adolatsizlikka qarshi kurashi, o'zining do'stlari va yaqinlari bilan birgalikda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi, uning qahramonligini yanada kuchaytiradi. U o'zining kuchli iroda va qat'iyati bilan xalqning umidlarini o'zida mujassam etadi.

Kumushbibi Otabekning sevgilisi sifatida, o'zining mustaqil va kuchli xarakteri bilan ajralib turadi. U Otabekning kurashlariga qo'shiladi va uning orzularini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Masalan, Kumushbibi Otabekning qiyinchiliklariga sabr-toqat bilan yondashadi va uning maqsadlariga erishishida yordam beradi. U o'zining sevgi va sadoqatini namoyon etgan holda, o'zbek ayolining kuchli ruhini va mustaqil fikrini aks ettiradi.

O'zbek oyim o'zida milliy urf – odatlarni mujassamlantirgani va o'z obro e'tibori, qiymati shu urf – odatlarning bayroqdori ekanligidaligini yaxshi biladi. Agar uning ongi va vujudidan urf – odatlar silsilasini sidirib tashlansa, u mahalla ko'nying boshqa oddiy hotinlaridan biriga aylanadi, dono eriga bo'lgan ta'siri ham bug'lanib ketadi. Shuning uchun ham u farzandining baxtini emas, balki o'zining ona sifatidagi go'yo haqoratlangan obrosini tiklashni o'ylaydi.

Yusufbek hoji O'zbek oyimdan farqli o'laroq el yurt taqdirini o'ylaydi, xalq tashvishi bilan yashaydi, o'lkaning kelajagi haqida qayg'uradi. U ana shu jihati bilan romandagi barcha qahramonlardan yuksakdir. Yozuvchi bu obrazi orqali tarix oldida

mas'uliyatli bo'lgan ajdodlarimizning rus bosqinchiligi arafasidagi holatini tasvirlaydi.

Zaynab asarning Kumush va Otabek singari markaziy qahramoni emas. U Yusufbek hoji va O'zbek oyim oilasiga Otabekning hotinlik ekanini bila turib, ya'ni kundshlik azoblariga rozi bo'lib tushkan. Shu ma'noda u o'zini kutayotkan taqdirga avvaldan rozi. Uning to'ygacha va to'ydan keying holatiga rozi bo'lishining o'zida sharq ayollariga hos milliy sifatlar – mutelik, ota–ona irodasiga bo'ysunish, taqdir oldida bo'yin egish bor. Kumushbibi bilan raqobatlashuvchi kundoshi sifatida, an'anaviy qadriyatlar va ko'pxotinlik masalalarini ko'taradi. U o'zining oila va jamiyatdagi o'rnini saqlab qolish uchun kurashadi. Masalan, Zaynabning Otabekka bo'lgan hissiyotlari va uning o'z o'rnini saqlab qolish uchun qilgan harakatlari, o'zbek jamiyatidagi ijtimoiy muammolarni ochib beradi. U orqali Qodiriy ko'pxotinlik va ayollarning jamiyatdagi o'rni haqida fikr yuritadi.

XULOSA

Qodiriy “O'tgan kunlar” asari bilan o'zbek romanchiligiga asos solibgina qolmay, milliylikimiz na'munalari qatorida tura oladigan, ajoyib, umrboqiy asarni yaratishga erishgan. A. Qodiriy birinchi romanini yozishga kirishishdan avval qardosh xalqlar adabiyotidagi romonjanridagi asarlarni o'rganibgina qolmay, uning milliy adabiyotimizda mavjud bo'lgan ildizlarini ham o'rganib chiqqan.

Katta ijtimoiy yukni o'z zimmasiga olmasin asarning Otabek va Kumush muhabbati asosiga qurilishi, xalq milliy qahramonlarining ko'pkina hususiyatlarining Otabek obrazida mujassamlantirilishi, qahramonning o'z muhabbati yo'lida juda ko'p imtihondan o'tishi, hatto o'limlarga duch kelib so'nggi lahzalarda ajal og'zidan qutilib chiqishi va boshqalar Qodiriyning xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalaridan haqida guvohi bo'lamiz.

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TURK VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA FITOMORF BIRLIKLAR ORQALI INSON OBRAZINING IFODALANISHI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu ilmiy maqola turk tilida fitonimik birliklar, asosan meva nomlari orqali inson obrazini ifodalashdagi ahamiyati haqida. Fitonimik lug'at orqali shaxsni obrazli nominatsiya qilish muammosi tilshunoslikda o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Uning lingvistik qiymatining sababi insonni o'zini o'rab turgan tirik tabiat sharoitida o'zini anglashning uzluksiz jarayonida yotadi. Ushbu jarayon fitosferani antropotsentrik talqin qilishning yangi shakllari bilan doimiy ravishda ta'minlanib, keng tarqalmoqda. Bir tomondan, u so'z boyligining barcha yangi qatlamlarini qamrab oladi, boshqa tomondan, turli darajadagi til darajalariga kirib boradi. Bu darajalarning eng qudratlisi - matn darajasi ham chetda qolmaydi.

Turk tilida inson qiyofasini aks ettirish, ularning xarakterlarini ochib berishda fitonim nomlari, ularning qo'llanilish darajasi va tilning so'z boyligiga e'tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, inson qiyofasi, obraz, portret, fitomorf birliklar, ijobiy, salbiy, tashqi ko'rinish, o'xshatish, obraz, muqobil, ekvivalent, ma'no ko'chishi.

В данной научной статье речь идет о значении фитонимических единиц турецкого языка, главным образом названий фруктов, в выражении образа человека. Проблема образной номинации человека посредством фитонимического словаря не утратила своей значимости в языкознании. Причина его языкового значения заключается в непрерывном процессе самосознания человека в окружающей его живой природе. Этот процесс постоянно поддерживается новыми формами антропоцентрической интерпретации фитосферы и широко распространяется. С одной стороны, оно охватывает все новые пласты лексики, с другой – проникает на разные уровни языка. Самый мощный из этих уровней — текстовый уровень.

Названия фитонимов, уровень их употребления и словарный запас языка обращаются во внимание при отражении образа человека в турецком языке и раскрытии его характера.

Ключевые слова: Язык, человеческий облик, образ, портрет, фитоморфные единицы, позитив, негатив, облик, сравнение, образ, альтернатива, эквивалент, передача смысла.

Abstract

This scientific article is about the significance of phytonymic units in Turkish, mainly fruit names, in expressing the human image. The problem of figurative nomination of a person through the phytonymic dictionary has not lost its importance in linguistics. The reason for its linguistic value lies in the continuous process of self-awareness of a person in the living nature that surrounds him. This process is constantly supported by new forms of anthropocentric interpretation of the phytosphere and is spreading widely. On the one hand, it covers all new layers of vocabulary, on the other hand, it penetrates to different levels of language. The most powerful of these levels is the text

level.

Phytonym names, the level of their use and the vocabulary of the language are paid attention to when reflecting the image of a person in the Turkish language and revealing their characters.

Keywords: Language, human image, image, portrait, positive, negative, appearance, simile, image, alternative, equivalent, transfer of meaning.

Kirish: Flora nomlari har qanday til lug'at tarkibining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Aynan unda xalq madaniyati, uning urf -odatlari, ramzlari, afsona va diniy qarashlari aks etadi. Shu bois xalqning hayotini o'simliklar dunyosisiz, tilini fitonimlarsiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Negaki, inson o'simliklarni nomlash, uni bilish orqali odam o'zining dunyo tasvirini yaratadi.

O'simlik nomlari fitonimikada o'zining o'rganish obyekti va predmetiga ega. O'simlik nomlari fitonimlar, ularning majmuyi fitonimiya deb yuritiladi.

Fitonimik lug'at orqali tushunchani obrazli nominatsiya qilish masalasi tilshunoslikda o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Uning lingvistik mohiyatida insonning o'zini o'rab turgan tirik tabiiy sharoitda o'zini anglashi yotadi. Ushbu jarayon fitosferani antropotsentrik talqin qilishning yangi shakllari bilan doimiy ravishda uyg'un kechadi. Bir tomondan, u lug'at tarkibining barcha yangi qatlamlarini qamrab oladi, ikkinchidan, turli darajadagi til qatlamlariga kirib boradi.

Madsad va vazifa: Mazkur maqolada fitonim nomlari bilan bog'liq ismlarning turk tili olam lisoniy manzarasini ifodalovchi vosita ekanligini dalillash maqsadida turk tilidagi fitomorf komparativ birliklarning qo'llanilishini tahlil qilish vazifasi qo'yilgan.

Usullar: Maqola mavzusini yoritishda tavsiflash, tasniflash, qiyoslash, lingvomadaniy tahlil usullaridan foydalanildi.

Natijalar va mulohaza: Yer kurrasining deyarli hamma qismida uchraydigan o'simliklarning tabiat va inson hayotidagi roli beqiyosdir. O'simliklar dunyosi uning inson hayotidagi ahamiyatini hisobga olgan holda, madaniy hayot uchun alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bu esa tilshunoslikda o'simliklarni leksik-semantik va lingvistik-madaniy jihatdan o'rganishni taqozo etadi. Inson yaratilgandan beri o'simliklar bilan aloqada bo'lgan. Ular gohida o'simliklardan oziq-ovqat sifatida, gohida esa o'z dardini davolash uchun dori sifatida foydalanishgan. Ikkala asosiy ehtiyojni ham qondiradigan o'simliklar vaqt o'tishi bilan qondirish ehtiyojlariga qarab yoki shakli o'xshashligi natijasida turli nomlar ola boshladi. Bu o'sish insonning vaqt o'tishi bilan boyib borayotgan so'z boyligiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi.²³ Inson hayoti flora dunyosiga katta e'tibor qaratadi. Fitonimlar qator tadqiqotchilarning e'tiborini jalb qilishda, ularni turli diskursda (adabiy, she'riy, ilmiy) ko'rib chiqish davom etmoqda. O'simliklar ko'p jihatdan tekshiriladi va bu tekshiruvlarga muvofiq ravishda nomlar berila boshlandi. Hozirda barcha o'simliklarni o'z nomlari mavjud. O'simliklarga nom berila

²³ Yasemin Y. Türkçe bitki adlarinin anlam bilimi açısından incelenmesi. doktora tezi. t.c. sakarya üniversitesi sosyal bilimler enstitüsü:2020.-S.98

boshlagandan keyin ularning nomlaridan insonlar o'zlari uchun ism tariqasida ham foydalana boshlashdi. Shuningdek, nutqda inson obrazining yaratilishida fitonimlarning roli ko'paydi.

Tirik tabiat obyektlari birliklari bilan shaxsni tavsiflashning muhim tomoni shundaki, inson uchun zarur bo'lgan fazilatlar muhim bo'lgan xususiyatlar va uning shaxsiyatini ochib beradigan xususiyatlar o'rtasida aniq chiziq chizish deyarli mumkin emas. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, odamning tashqi va ichki ko'rinishini tushunishda, inson tafakkurining bir til darajasidan ikkinchisiga harakatlanishiga e'tibor qaratib, tarkibiy jihatdan murakkab "shaxs" tushunchasini tahlil obyekti qilib olish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Ushbu jarayon ma'lum bir til imkoniyatlariga bo'ysungan holda, uni ko'p darajali talqin qilishning bitta murakkab tizimini keltirib chiqaradi.

N.Pazliddinova o'zining "O'zbek tili fitonimlarining leksik-semantik xususiyatlari" nomli tadqiqotida hosilni odam va uning tana a'zolariga o'xshatish asosida yuzaga kelgan fitonimlar: "Kelinbarmoq"/"Kelinbarmoq husayni", "Kulja", "Malikaning kipriklari" (uzum navlari), "Qariqiz" (qovun navi) kabilar, odamlarga xos belgi-xususiyatlarga nisbat berish asosida hosil qilingan fitonimlar: Juvonmarg handalak (handalak navi), "A'lochi" (behi navi), "Go'zal" (bug'doy, olcha, kungaboqar, olma navlari) kabilar haqida to'xtalib o'tgan²⁴.

Dunyo tillarida inson tashqi ko'rinishini ifodalashda meva nomlari ham faol ishtirok etadi. Mevalar bilan bog'liq qiyoslar har bir xalqning yashash tarzidan kelib chiqqan holda belgilanadi. Turk xalqida *nok, zaytun, xurmo, tog' pista, qovun, anor* kabi mevalar inson tashqi qiyofasini aks ettirishda keng qo'llansa, o'zbek millati uchun esa *olma, jiyda, yong'oq, bodom, tarvuz* kabilar ahamiyatlidir.

Turk lingvomadaniyatida armut//nok (murut) so'zi inson tabiatini aks ettirishda eng keng qo'llanadi. Xususan, "armut gibi" o'xshatishli birikmasi yordamida "gap tushunmaydigan, anqov kishi"ga nisbatan ishlatiladi. *Armut gibi ne demek? Çok anlayışsız, bön*²⁵. Armut mevasi yordamida ko'pincha salbiy xarakterli kishilar obrazi yaratiladi. Dangasa, biror ish qilmasdan foyda kutadigan, rizqni osmondan tushadi deb o'tiradigan odamlarga nisbatan turk olam lisoniy manzarasida "*armut piş, ağzıma düş*" iborasi ham ishlatiladi. Bu o'zbek lingvomadaniyatidagi "olma pish og'zimga tush" iborasining aynan o'zidir. Bu esa turklar tafakurida armut//nok (murut) bilan bir xil ma'no kasb etuvchi hech bir mehnat sarflamasdan bir nima kutadigan odamlarga nisbatan ishlatiluvchi tekinxo'r obrazini ifodalashini ta'kidlash joizdir.

O'zbek va turk tillarida meva nomlarining o'shatish etaloni sifatida qo'llanishi ham ko'p uchraydi. Bunday o'xshatish etalonlariga "gilos", "olma", "yong'oq" kabi meva nomlarini misol sifatida keltirish mumkin.

²⁴Пазлитдинова Н. Ўзбек тили фитонимларининг лексик-семантик хусусиятлари // Филол.фан. номз. дисс. Автореф. – Фарғона, 2018. -Б. 15.

²⁵<https://www.nedirnedemek.com/armut-gibi-ne-demek>

Turk tilida “ayva göbekli” metaforasi orqali qorni pastga osilgan kishining tasviri ifodalanadi. Ayva- bu behi, behi fitonimining shakli turk tilida qorni osilgan odam obrazi uchun qo'llanadi.

Har ikki tilda *kiraz // gilos* fitonimi keng tarqalgan. Uning yordamida qip-qizil lablar gilosga qiyoslangan. Masalan, *kiraz dudakli//gilos dudoqli*, ya'ni *lablari gilosday* qiyosi orqali lablari qizil va qalin bo'lgan ayollar ta'rifi uchun qo'llangan. *Dildor gilosday qizil, chiroyli lablariga yoyilgan tabassum bilan boshini silkidi. Oltinrang sochlari yelkalari uzra sochilib ketgan, qayrilma kiprikli ko'zlarini ochib-yumganda gilosday qizil lablari o'z-o'zidan jilmayib qo'yadigan qo'g'irchoqqa, ochig'i, hammamizning havasimiz keldi*²⁶. O'zbek xalq lingvomadaniyatida, shuningdek, “*labing gilosga o'xshar, ko'zing charosga o'xshar*” deb aytiluvchi qo'shiq misralari bor. Bu yerda lab gilosga o'xshatish asnosida ko'z charosga, ya'ni uzumning qora rangli naviga qiyoslanmoqda. Turklarda esa qorachadan kelgan odam ta'rifida *üzüm gibi* o'xshatishi qo'llanadi va bunda qora rangli uzum ma'nosi faollashtirilgan. Shuningdek, *‘çöpsüz üzüm’ yakın akrabaları hayatta olmayan kişi, üzüntü verici bir şeymiş gibi dursa da özellikle zengin koca arayan hanımlar için çift katlı ekmek kadayıfi durumudur*. Cho'psiz uzum birikmasi hech kimi yo'q yolg'iz ayolni ifoda etadi²⁷. *Üzüm gibi* turklarda qorachadan kelgan ma'nosida keluvchi bu metafora turk tilida asosan qorachadan kelgan qariya kishini bildirsa, o'zbek tilida bu ko'rinish uzumning quritilgani - *mayizday* ifodasi yordamida beriladi.

Elma//olma har ikki til egalari tafakkurida deyarli bir xil komparativ ma'noda keladi. Masalan, *elma yanakli//olma yuzli* “yuzlari qip-qizil olmaga o'xshagan kishilar”ga nisbatan turk tilida ham o'zbek tilida ham ishlatiladi. O'zbek folkloridan joy olgan “Yor-yor”larda ham, aytishuvlarda ham qizlarning yuzini olmaga o'xshatish keng tarqalgan. Ayniqsa, “*Eronning olmasidek qip-qizil yuzlari*” o'xshatishli birikmasi xalq orasida mashhur.

Turklarda ko'proq ayollarning go'zalligi anor mevaiga o'xshatiladi: “Nar çiçeği” nomli she'rlari ham bor.

Canım kurban yoluna
Takıver yar koluna
*Nar Çiçeğim, Yar Çiçeğim*²⁸.

O'zbek tilida “anordek yuzi” birikmasi ham mavjud bo'lib, bu bilan sog'lom insonlarning yal-yal yonib turgan yuzlari gavdalantiriladi. Qip-qizil, qon rangida; qizarmoq, qizil tusini olmoq kabi o'xshatishlarda *anorday* etalonidan foydalaniladi. Miryusuf Xilvatiy banoras to'ning keng etaklari orasida oyoqlari chalishib, o'rnidan

²⁶Маҳмудов Н., Худойберганова Д. Ўзбек тили ўхшатишларининг изоҳли луғати – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2013.-Б.56.

²⁷<https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/mahmure/ruyada-uzum-gormek-ne-anlama-gelir-ruyada-uzum-yemek-tabiri-41400491>

²⁸<https://onedio.com/haber/serdar-ortac-nar-çiçeğim-sarki-sözleri>.

turdi, qo'ltig'idan ipak matoga o'ralgan bir kitobchani olib ochdi va anorday qip-qizil, yum-yumaloq yuzi ilhomdan lov-lov yonib, ovozi hayajondan titrab, o'qiy ketdi (O.Yoqubov. Ulug'bek xazinas).

Turk xalqi lingvomadaniyatida zaytun fitonimi katta o'rin tutadi. Zaytun qora bo'lishi bilan birga, ham foydali ham mazali bo'lgani uchun *zeytin gibi* o'xshatishli birikmasi qorachadan kelgan, istarali qizlarni ta'riflashda ishlatiladi.

Shuningdek, quruq meva nomlari har ikki xalq lingvomadaniyatida keng foydalaniladigan inson obrazini ifodalovchi fitomorf birliklar hisoblanadi. Fıstık yong'og'i kishilar orasida sevgilisini yoxud yosh bolani erkalab chaqirishda *fıstıgım* shaklida qo'llanadi, shirinligiga qiyoslanadi. Xalq orasida *çekirdekten yetişme* iborasi ham keng tarqalgan bo'lib, tug'ma iste'dodli insonga ko'ra nisbatlanadi. Bu fitonim çekirdek-pista bo'lib, turk xalqi yashash tarzida ajralmas o'ringa egadir.

Umuman olganda, meva nomlari orqali shaxsning u yoki bu xususiyatini tasvirlash yaratish til imkoniyatlarining qanchalik kengligini ko'rsatib beradi, ta'sirchanlikni oshiradi hamda tinglovchiga shaxs haqida aniq taassurot qoldiradi va idrok qilinishini osonlashtiradi.

Insonni xarakterlash uchun meva nomlaridan foydalanish jarayoni qadimiy hisoblanadi. Inson mavjud bo'lgan paytdan boshlab tabiat bilan chambarchas birlikda yashab, atrofdagi daraxt va o'simliklarga turli xil munosabatda bo'lgan. Tabiat va inson uyg'unligi dunyoning barcha lisoniy manzaralarida universaldir.

Har ikki til tafakkuridagi daraxt va mevalar bilan bog'liq fitonimlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, inson ijobiy xususiyatlarini aks ettirishda ko'proq mevali daraxtlarga qiyoslanilsa, kishining salbiy qiyofasini ifodalashda esa asosan, daraxtning kesilgan tanasi, o'tin yoki to'nka bilan bog'liq birliklar orqali ifodalanadi.

Ushbu turdagi qiyosiy tadqiqotlar taqqoslangan tillarning milliy-madaniy xususiyatlarini, shuningdek ma'lum bir tilda so'zlashuvchilarning milliy mentaliteti va dunyoqarashining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga imkon beradi.

Shunday qilib, fitonimik nominatsiyalar o'zbek va turk tillarida insonning ichki dunyosi va tashqi ko'rinishini belgilashda keng qo'llanadi va ba'zi hollarda insonning har qanday xususiyatlariga (tashqi qiyofasi, aqliy qobiliyatlari, ichki hissiy holati, Yoshi, kasbi, ijtimoiy holati) o'ziga xos standart bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Har ikki til tafakkuridagi daraxt va mevalar bilan bog'liq fitonimlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, inson ijobiy xususiyatlarini aks ettirishda ko'proq mevali daraxtlarga qiyoslanilsa, uning tashqi ko'rinishi manzarali daraxt nomlariga qiyoslanadi. Insonning ijobiy yoki salbiy xarakterlari esa shirin va achchiq meva nomlari yordamida ham aks ettiriladi.

Xulosa: Botanik nomlar, ayniqsa, meva nomlari bilan bog'liq ismlar insonga tabiiylik va go'zallik qo'shadi. Botanika nomlari nafaqat noyob va abadiydir, balki ular atrof-muhit bilan aloqani aks ettiradi va tabiatga muhabbatni uyg'otadi. Atirgul va

yasemin kabi klassik variantlardan tortib, noodatiy nomlarga qadar har qanday afzallik va uslubga mos keladigan botanika nomi mavjud. Inson shaxsiyatiga botanika nomini qo'shish tabiiy dunyoni hurmat qilish va dunyoga hayrat va minnatdorchilik tuyg'usini uyg'otishning bir usuli hisoblanadi. Meva nomlari orqali inson obrazini ifodalash til imkoniyatlarining qanchalik kengligini ko'rsatadi. Shunday qilib, ismlarni ko'rib chiqayotganda, an'anaviy variantlardan tashqari mavjud botanika nomlarining keng doirasini o'rganish kerak bo'ladi. Buni o'zbek tilida ham turk tilida ham tatbiq qilish esa ikki til doirasida so'z boyligining kengayishiga zamin yaratadi.

Mevaning madaniyatda talqin qilinishi esa insonlar orasidagi mazmunli munosabatlarni namoyish etadi. Bu timsol sevgi, do'stlik, hurmat va barqarorlik kabi xos xususiyatlarni ifodalaydi. Bunday muhim timsoldan kelib chiqadigan madaniyatlar insonlarning bir-birlari bilan munosabatlari va odamlarga qarshi adabiyotini namoyon etishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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TARJIMADA ADEKVATLIK TUSHUNCHASINING MOHIYATI

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Annotatsiya

Xususan, ushbu maqola quyidagilarni qamrab oladi: tarjimashunoslikda asliyat birliklari; Adekvatlik va ekvivalentlik atamalari; Maqollarni tarjima qilishda ekvivalentlik; Ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik tushunchalari o‘rtasidagi asosiy farqlar.

Kalit so‘zlar: Adekvatlik, ekvivalentlik, lingvistik tarjima, o‘quv tarjimasi, tarjima, tarjimon.

Аннотация

В частности, в этой статье рассматриваются: единицы оригинала в переводоведении; термины адекватность и эквивалентность; эквивалентность при переводе пословиц; основные различия между понятиями эквивалентности и адекватности.

Ключевые слова: адекватность, эквивалентность, лингвистический перевод, учебный перевод, перевод, переводчик.

Annotation

Specifically, this article covers: source units in translation studies; the terms adequacy and equivalence; equivalence in the translation of proverbs; the main differences between the concepts of equivalence and adequacy.

Keywords: adequacy, equivalence, linguistic translation, educational translation, translation, translator.

Bugungi kunda tarjimashunoslikda asliyat birliklari funksiyasini aniqlash, qiyosiy tadqiq qilish va shu funsiyani bir tildan ikkinchi tilga o‘girishning nazariy asoslarini ishlab chiqish kabi ustuvor yo‘nalishlar soha olimlarining diqqat-e’tiborini tortib, katta bahslarga sabab bo‘lib kelmoqda hamda badiiy tarjimaning mukammal bo‘lishida ekvivalentlik asosiy ahamiyatga egami yoki adekvatlik kabi masalalar o‘z yechimini kutmoqda.[1.160] Bundan anglashimiz mumkinki, adekvatlik nafaqat sinxron tarjimada, balki badiiy tarjimada ham alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Adekvatlik va ekvivalentlik atamalari etimologik nuqtai nazardan bir-biri bilan bog‘liq bo‘lib, ular lotincha “adeque – teng, bir-xil” shuningdek shakliga borib taqaladi. Lekin tarjima nazariyasida ular turli ma'nolarga ega bo‘ldi.[2.17-21] Shu nuqtai nazardan, bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog‘liq ikkala tushuncha o‘rtasidagi farqni ko‘rsatib o‘tamiz: 1) Adekvatlik deganda lot “adequatus”- to‘liq, aynan mos, mutanosib, izchil, haqiqiy va bir xil ma'nolarini beradi. 2) Ekvivalentlik esa tarjima qilingan matnning asl matnga eng yaqin mos kelishi yoki bo‘lmasa lotincha “equivalens” so‘zidan olingan “teng kuchli”, “bir xil ma'noda” ekanligini bildiradi.” Endi yuqorida ta'kidlaganimizdek, adekvatlik va ekvivalentlik masalalari tarjimashunos olimlar Fedorov A.V., Komissarov, Shveyser A.D., va boshqa ko‘plab dunyo miqyosidagi tilshunos olimlar diqqat-e’tiborida bo‘lgan hamda shu masalalar

bo'yicha ilmiy nazariyalar vujudga kelgan. Jumladan, adekvatlik deganda, tadqiqotchi N.V.Shamova optimal tarjimaga olib boradigan yo'l, optimal tarjima yechimini topish yo'lidir va shuning uchun u ekvivalent tarjimaga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan tarjima jarayonidir,- deb fikr yuritadi. [3. 171-179] Shuni ta'kidlash o'rinliki, olimlar "adekvat tarjima" XX asrning 60 yillarida tilshunos olimlar I.I.Revzin va V.Yu.Rozensveyg tomonidan qo'llanilganligini ta'kidlab o'tadi. Adekvat tarjima deganda ular "to'la xuquqli tarjima" ni tushunadilar, uning ajralib turadigan xususiyatlari – asliyat matnining mazmunini to'liq uzatish va tarkibini ekvivalent vositalar orqali uzatishdir. Ushbu mezonlarga javob beradigan matn tarjimalari to'liq adekvatli, ya'ni ekvivalentli hisoblangan. Shu nuqtai nazardan bu tushunchalar sinonim deb topildi va bu borada A. Shamova, taniqli olim, tarjimon A.V.Fedorovning ushbu tushunchalar bo'yicha qarashlaridan kelib chiqqan holda, manba matn va tarjima qilingan matn o'rtasidagi tofovutni ko'rib chiqayotganda ikkita tushuncha "formalizm" va "adekvatlik" mavjud ekanligini va adekvatlik "to'liqlik" degan ma'noni anglatadi, biroq bu aslida ekvivalentlik hisoblanadi, deya fikr bildiradi. [4.170] Formalizm tushunchasi tarjima sohasida xorijiy til matnini so'zma-so'z to'g'ridan-to'g'ri uzatish holatiga nisbatan qo'llanilgan. Fedorovning fikricha, "so'zma-so'z tarjima har doim asl nusxaning ma'nosini yoki tarjima qilingan tilning to'g'riligini yoki ikkalasini ham buzishga xizmat qiladi. Formalizm tushunchasi bu holatda qo'llanilishi o'rinlidir, ammo u shaklning mazmundan ajralish tushunchasi sifatida ancha kengroqdir va shaklning ma'lum elementlarini o'z-o'zidan, tashqarida yetqazishga intilayotgan barcha holatlarga nisbatan qo'llanilishi mumkin, ya'ni tarjimon o'z vazifasidan tashqarida butunning mazmuniga va shaklning boshqa elementlariga e'tibor bermaydi, ya'ni shaklni mazmunidan ajralgan holda yoki shaklning ayrim elementlarini boshqalaridan ajratilgan holda va umuman mazmunidan ajratilgan holda takrorlaydi. Tarjimada formalizمنىning namoyon bo'lishi uning stilistik funksiyalaridan qat'iy nazar – asl nusxaning faqat ma'lum xususiyatlari ta'kidlanganda, arxaizmlar arxaizm bo'lib, varvarizmlar-varvarizm bo'lib tarjima qilinadi.

Maqollarni tarjima qilish jarayonida ulardan ba'zi birlariga ekvivalent topish mushkul. Masalan: A friend in court is better than a penny in purse – Sudda turib bergan do'st hamyondagi bir tiyindan yaxshiroq so'zma-so'z o'zbek tiliga tarjimasi. Suddagi do'st cho'ntakdagi chaqadan afzal. Ushbu tarjimada "penny" so'zi faqat inglizlarga xos bo'lib pul muomalasida qo'llaniladi. Maqolni o'zbek tiliga Boylik-boylik emas, birlik boylikdir deb tarjima qilish maqsadga muvofiqdir. A friend's eye is a good mirror so'zma-so'z o'zbek tiliga tarjimasi: Do'stning nigohi yaxshi ko'zgudir. O'zbek tilida Do'st achitib gapirar, dushman – kuldirib. "Erkin tarjima"da biz tarjima til me'yorlarida nomuvofiqlikni uchratmaymiz, ammo asl matnning ma'nosini o'zboshimchalik bilan talqin qilish holatlari ro'y berishi mumkin. Masalan: "She was smiling – Uning yuzi yorqin tabassum bilan to'ldi". To'g'ri tarjima: U tabassum qilayotgan edi. Binobarin,

tarjimaning adekvatligi deganda qoidaga asosan tarjimaning "to'liqligi"ni nazarda tutamiz, ya'ni ko'plab manba tilidagi matnning tarjima qilinishi kerak bo'lgan til matniga to'liq mos kelishini tushunamiz. Tarjimaning adekvatligi tarjima jarayonida asl til shaklining ma'nosi va to'g'riligini saqlab qolishdan iborat bo'ladi (Lopatin M.A.). Badiiy tarjimada ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik tamoyillari quyidagilar bilan chambarchas bog'liq:

- Tilning tabiati qanday tushuniladi;
- Asliyat va tarjima (asliyat)tillar o'rtasidagi munosobatlarning tabiati;
- Madaniy tofovutlarga munosabat;
- Tarjima tilida asliyat tildagi estetikaning ustunligi.

Adekvat tarjima - bu ancha noaniq termin bo'lib, asl nusxaning barcha belgilari va shakllarining tarjima tiliga o'tkazilishining yuqori darajasini bildiradi.

Adekvatlik tushunchasi tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyotida muhokama qilinadigan eng muhim vazifalardan biridir. Zamonaviy tarjimashunoslikka asos solingan 50-60-yillarda adekvatlik tushunchasi asl nusxaga mutlaq semantik muvofiqlik nisbatiga asoslanadi. Shundan kelib chiqqan holda, adekvatlik semantik to'liqlik va aniqlik toifalariga qisqartirildi va stilistik ekvivalentlik bilan to'ldiriladi.

Amalda lingvistik, leksik, grammatik shakllardagi farq, tarjima qilib bo'lmaydigan voqelik va o'rganilayotgan tilda ekvivalenti bo'lmagan frazeologik iboralar mavjudligi sababli to'laqonli adekvat tarjima qilish mumkin emas.

Bu muammo bilan shug'ullanuvchi har bir olim adekvatlik terminiga o'ziga xos ta'rif beradi. Shulardan biri Y.I.Retzker shunday deb yozadi: "Adekvatlik mezonni faqat asl nusxada tasvirlangan voqelik zarrasiga muvofiqlik bo'lishi mumkinligi sababli, til vositalarining ekvivalentligi, agar o'ziga xoslik bilan emas, balki olingan natijaning asl nusxaning ta'siriga maksimal yaqinlashishi bilan aniqlanadi. Yuqori mahorat darajasida amalga oshirilgan har qanday tarjima tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, til vositalarining ekvivalentligini o'rnatish uchun asos rasmiy emas, faqat funksional bo'lishi mumkin".

Adekvat tarjima - bu ma'lum bir maqsadga erishiladigan manba va tarjima matnlarining nisbati ("lingvistik tarjima", "o'quv tarjimasi"). Adekvatlik jarayon sifatida tarjimaga qaratilgan. "Adekvatlik" termini "ekvivalentlik" termini bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik tushunchalari o'rtasidagi asosiy farqlar:

Ekvivalentlik tarjima natijasiga qaratiladi, adekvatlik tillararo kommunikativ akt oqimining shartlari, kommunikativ vaziyatga (jarayonga) mos keladigan tarjima strategiyasini tanlash bilan bog'liq.

Ekvivalentlik munosabati semantik va pragmatik darajalarga cho'zilsa, biz asl va tarjima matnlari o'rtasida to'liq ekvivalentlik mavjudligini etirof etishimiz mumkin. Ekvivalentlik munosabati semiotik darajalardan faqat bittasini - pragmatikni qamrab

olsa, matnlarning ekvivalentligi qisman bo'ladi. Adekvatlik tarjimaning haqiqiy amaliyotiga asoslangan bo'lib, u ko'pincha muhosasiz xarakterga ega bo'lib, ikkilamchi aloqada paydo bo'lgan maxsus sharoitlar (reseptorning tabiati va kutishlari, uning madaniy va boshqa farqlari) foydasiga asl nusxadan sezilarli og'ishlarga imkon beradi.). Ikkilamchi aloqa jarayonida muloqotning maqsadi ko'pincha o'zgarib turadi, bu muqarrar ravishda aniqlikni talab qiladi

Asliyat va tarjima matnlarning to'liq ekvivalentligidan chetga chiqish. Bu aynan yangi madaniy muhitning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda an'anaviy ravishda bepul tarjima qilishga ruxsat berilgan badiiy asarlar (romanlar, p'esalar, filmlar va boshqalar) nomlarini tarjima qilishda namoyon bo'ladi.

To'liq ekvivalentlik asl matnni to'liq ko'chirishni nazarda tutadi. Shunday qilib, ekvivalentlik tarjima uchun eng yuqori talabdir. Adekvatlik tarjimaning haqiqiy amaliyotiga asoslanadi, bu ko'pincha asl nusxaning butun mazmunini to'liq uzatishga imkon bermaydi. Adekvatlik talabi optimaldir.

Tarjimaning "adekvatligi" haqida gapirganda, qoida tariqasida, biz tarjimaning "to'liqligi"ni nazarda tutamiz, ya'ni, asliyat tilidagi matnning tarjima qilmoqchi bo'lgan til matniga to'liq mos kelishi. Tarjimaning adekvatligi tarjima jarayonida asl til shaklining ma'nosi va to'g'riligini saqlab qolishdan iborat. Ushbu muammoning oldingi tadqiqotlarida tarjimaning "sodiqliqi" atamasi ishlatilgan, ammo yetarli darajada ilmiy bo'lmagan bu tushuncha tarjimaning "adekvatligi" ta'rifi bilan almashtirildi.

Noto'g'ri tarjima odatda kichik stilistik noaniqliklardan tortib jiddiyroq xatolargacha - tarjima qilingan matnning ma'nosini buzishgacha bo'lgan turli darajadagi muvaffaqiyasizlikka ega. Tarjimada eng ko'p uchraydigan xatolar - bu asl tilning matnini izlash yoki so'zma-so'z tarjima deb ataladigan narsa va asl matn mazmunini erkin talqin qilish, bu asliyat va tarjima tillari o'rtasida katta tafovutlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Tarjimadagi bu ikki cheklov tarixiy jihatdan mustahkamlangan, eng keng tarqalgan tarjima turlari. "So'zma-so'z tarjima" tushunchasi salbiy ma'noga ega, chunki bu tarjima, qoida tariqasida, asl tilning grammatik, leksik va stilistik me'yorlarini buzadi. Quyida ayrim misollarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

I'm not a woman you can trust – Men siz ishonadigan ayol emasman.

She's bold today! – U bugun dadil.

There were men and women at the bus station – Avtobus bekatida erkaklar va ayollar bor edi.

Tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyotida tarjima adekvatligi termini bilan bir qatorda tarjima ekvivalentligi tushunchasi ham keng qo'llanila boshlandi. Bu yerda gap grammatik, leksik, pragmatik darajadagi ekvivalentni tanlash haqida ketmoqda.

Ekvivalentlik sof rasmiy bo'lishi mumkin, bu bizni ingliz tilidan o'zbek tiliga va aksincha, so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish imkoniyatidan foydalanishimizga asoslanadi.

Rasmiy ekvivalentlikka har qanday til darajasida erishish mumkin:

-morfologik darajada: “-ing” qo'shimchasi so'zning oxiriga qo'shib, u sifatdosh vazifasini bajaradi, “-ing” o'zbek tilidagi ekvivalentligi “-sh”, “-ish” qo'shimchalari hisoblanadi. Masalan, reading leksik birligining o'zbek tilidagi ekvivalenti o'qish hisoblanadi;

-leksik darajada: window – deraza, drug store – dorixona;

-gap darajasida: He is distressed – U iztirobda.

Ekvivalentlikning til sathi darajalari bo'yicha quyidagi turlari mavjud:

denotativ: bag – sumka, note-book – daftar:

konnotativ, nutqning to'liq ifodasi, semantik soyalar, subtekst bilan bog'liq: old chap – chol.

janrga mansublik va nutq registrini saqlash bilan bog'liq stilistik sath: eyes – ko'z, lips – og'iz, gold – oltin;

me'yoriy, bu ma'lum bir tilning me'yorlari va qoidalariga rioya qilishni nazarda tutadi (grammatik jihatdan to'g'rilik, leksik darajadagi muvofiqlik va boshqalar); He lives in this house – U shu uyda yashaydi.

kommunikativ harakatning tabiatini va muloqot muvaffaqiyatini aks ettiruvchi kommunikativ-pragmatik daraja: Villain! – Razil!

Ekvivalentlik tarjimashunoslikdagi eng asosiy kategoriyalardan biri xisoblanib, u asliyat tilining til sathlari bo'yicha barcha lisoniy birliklarining tarjima tiliga ham o'zaro muvofiq bo'lishi nazarda tutiladi.

Tarjimashunoslikda adekvatlik tushunchasi me'yor sifatida qo'llaniladi, u asosan qardosh tillarga amalga oshirilgan tarjimalar adekvatlik maqomini olish mumkin. Bir tizimga mansub bo'lmagan o'zbek va ingliz tillari orasida adekvat maqomdagi tarjimalar uchramaydi. Chunki adekvat tarjima bo'lishi uchun ikki til orasida uslubiy, kontekstual, semantic, struktur, fonetik va madaniy omillar bir biriga to'laligicha mos kelishi kerak. Bundanda asosiy sabab bu o'zbek va ingliz tiliboshqa boshqa til oilalariga mansub va ular orasida judayam kata morfologik tafovut mavjud. Shuning natijasida esa adekvatlik maqomi mazkur tillarda deyarli uchramaydi.

Tarjimon asliyatdagi birliklar va nutq bo'laklarini o'girar ekan, tarjimasida ekvivalent variantlarni tanlaydi. Ularni asliyat bilan qiyoslab, tanlangan tarjima varianti ustida ishlab, uni kommunikativ jihatdan muvozanat holatiga keltiradi. Ushbu jarayon tarjimondan tegishli bilim va mahoratni talab qiladi.

Asliyat va tarjima mazmuni orasidagi real munosabatlarni qaror toptirish tarjimonga ikki matn o'rtasida umumiylik chizig'ini tortishga, maksimal darajada turli tildagi matnlarning ma'noviy yaqinligini ta'minlashga imkon beradi. Shu orqali tarjima sifatiga erishiladi. Tarjima matnining asliyatga nisbatan yaqinligini ta'minlovchi tarjima ekvivalent tarjima deyiladi.

Tadqiqotda ekvivalentlik hodisa sifatida tahlil qilinadi. Chunki agar uni

kategoriya sifatida qabul qilinsa unda darhol majburiy komponenti paydo bo'ladi, agar hodisa deb qabul qilinsa, o'sha paydo bo'lishi majburiy bo'lmagan birlik sifatida, bu tushuncha va bu voqeadan majburiylik belgisi yo'qoladi.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CULTURAL SENSITIVITY IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

2-sho'ba

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til o'rganish jarayonida madaniy sezgirlikning muhim roli yoritilgan bo'lib, u til bilimlari bilan samarali muloqot o'rtasidagi tafovutni bartaraf etishda muhim vosita sifatida qaraladi. Madaniy xabardorlik o'rganuvchilarga turli ijtimoiy kontekstlarda to'g'ri va mos muloqot qilish imkonini beradi, shu orqali idiomatik iboralar, tana harakati (body language) va suhbat odoblarini chuqurroq anglashga yordam beradi. Maqolada til faqatgina aloqa vositasi emas, balki xalqning qadriyatlarini, tarixi va ijtimoiy me'yorlarini aks ettiruvchi hodisa ekanligi ta'kidlanadi. Madaniy kompetensiyaga ega bo'lmagan o'rganuvchilar tilning amaliy jihatlari tushunishda qiynalishlari mumkin. Shu bois, maqolada til o'rgatish jarayoniga madaniy elementlarni kiritish zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy xabardorlik, til o'rganish, tana harakati, idiomatik iboralar, suhbat odobi, madaniy kontekst.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность культурной чувствительности в процессе овладения иностранным языком, как ключевого фактора, способствующего преодолению разрыва между знанием языка и эффективным общением. Культурная осведомлённость помогает учащимся адекватно взаимодействовать в различных социальных контекстах, лучше понимать идиоматические выражения, язык тела и нормы речевого этикета. Язык представлен не только как средство общения, но и как отражение истории, ценностей и культурных норм общества. Недостаток культурной компетентности может затруднить использование языка в реальных ситуациях. Автор подчёркивает необходимость включения культурных компонентов в процесс преподавания языка для формирования полноценной коммуникативной компетенции учащихся.

Ключевые слова: культурная осведомлённость, изучение языка, язык тела, идиоматические выражения, речевой этикет, культурный контекст.

Annotation: This article explores the vital role of cultural sensitivity in language acquisition, emphasizing its impact on bridging the gap between linguistic knowledge and effective communication. Cultural awareness enhances learners' ability to engage appropriately in diverse social contexts by deepening their understanding of idiomatic expressions, non-verbal cues, and conversational etiquette. The article argues that language is not only a tool for communication but also a mirror of a community's values, history, and social norms. Without cultural competence, learners may struggle with pragmatic aspects of language use, hindering their overall communicative success. The study highlights the importance of integrating cultural components into language instruction to foster meaningful and contextually appropriate communication skills.

Keywords: cultural awareness, language acquisition, body language, idiomatic expressions, conversational etiquette, cultural context.

INTRODUCTION

Learning a language is commonly thought of as the process of becoming proficient in vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation, but cultural awareness is an important aspect that is frequently disregarded. The values, customs, and social mores of the people who use a language are all reflected in it. Cultural sensitivity is therefore necessary for clear understanding and successful communication in any language. Learners could overlook the subtleties of discourse if they don't comprehend the cultural context, which could result in unpleasant interactions or misunderstandings. Language learners can improve their ability to traverse a variety of social contexts, speak honestly, and develop a better understanding of the language they are learning by adopting cultural awareness. In addition to improving communication, this linguistic and cultural fusion promotes tolerance for difference and a more global perspective. Understanding the social, political, and historical backgrounds of English-speaking communities is a component of cultural awareness. It is essential to understand the subtleties of communication, including idioms and nonverbal clues, and eventually to forge closer bonds with native speakers. It is the capacity to comprehend and negotiate the variations in customs, values, and communication styles among English-speaking cultures. It entails realising that English is a collection of dialects, accents, and regional variants shaped by the history and identity of its speakers rather than a single language.

Adopting cultural sensitivity helps students:

- Recognise colloquial terms in context.
- Modify your communication methods to suit various contexts.
- Handle regional pronunciations and accents.
- Develop deep connections with speakers from various backgrounds.

METHODS

To promote a more profound and genuine comprehension of a language,

cultural sensitivity must be incorporated into language learning strategies. Grammar, vocabulary, and syntax are the main topics of traditional language acquisition; however, adding cultural components to these approaches improves communication skills and enriches the learning process. The following are some successful strategies for integrating cultural sensitivity into language learning:

➤ **Immersion Education:** Immersion is one of the best methods to cultivate cultural understanding. Interacting with native speakers, taking part in cultural activities, or even visiting a nation where the language is spoken are all ways for language learners to interact with the language. This offers a chance to learn about social conventions, everyday practices, and the language's background.

➤ **Media and Literature:** Students are better able to comprehend the language in its cultural context when they are exposed to films, music, novels, and television shows from the target culture. These resources frequently contain humour, colloquial language, and allusions to local customs that are hard to master from textbooks alone.

➤ **Cultural Debates and Discussions:** Cultural topics including food, festivals, history, and social issues, can be discussed in language learning programs. By taking part in these conversations, students can investigate cultural variations and broaden their comprehension of how language expresses social values.

➤ **Role-playing and Real-Life Scenarios:** Learners can practise language use in many social contexts by simulating real-life scenarios, such as ordering meals, bargaining, or striking up a conversation. Communication effectiveness can be increased and misconceptions can be avoided by being aware of cultural differences in formality, humour, and politeness.

➤ **Study of Non-Verbal Communication:** Since non-verbal communication can have diverse cultural connotations, it is essential to comprehend body language, facial expressions, and gestures. Accurate interpretation and response to non-verbal cues are ensured when these elements are taught in conjunction with verbal communication.

➤ **Cooperation and Cultural Exchange:** Participating in exchange programs or forming alliances with native speakers gives students the chance to see and experience cultural customs up close. Group conversations, dance lessons, and cooking workshops are examples of collaborative activities that promote a stronger bond between language and culture.

RESULTS

Beyond only improving language proficiency, there are some advantages to integrating cultural understanding into language study. Cultural context integration in language instruction has a variety of benefits, including improved communication and personal development. The main findings are as follows:

Learners can use the language more naturally and appropriately in a variety of circumstances when they are aware of other cultures. Learners can prevent

misunderstandings and communicate in ways that are accurate and courteous by being aware of cultural quirks, including formality, politeness, humour, and non-verbal clues. As a result, conversations with native speakers are more fruitful and significant.

Learners can apply new vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and grammatical structures to real-world scenarios when they comprehend the cultural context in which a language is spoken. Because of this link between language and culture, the information is simpler to remember and keep, which leads to

DISCUSSION

In language acquisition, cultural sensitivity is frequently viewed as a secondary issue, with a focus on vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. But incorporating cultural awareness is not only advantageous; it is necessary for achieving true language proficiency. In this conversation, we examine how cultural sensitivity affects language learning and why it ought to be regarded as a basic component of language learning.

Language and culture are closely related. The meanings and connotations of words, idioms, and even grammar structures are frequently derived from the speakers' cultural backgrounds. For example, depending on the cultural context, a single term may mean several things. Gaining an understanding of a language's culture aids learners in recognising these nuances, which enhances their capacity for self-expression and interpersonal comprehension. Without this understanding, students might not be able to access the deeper levels of meaning that enhance and improve communication.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, cultural sensitivity is a crucial component of language acquisition that should not be disregarded. Understanding the cultural context in which a language is spoken is essential to properly mastering it, even though learning vocabulary and grammar is also important. By assisting students in navigating social conventions, preventing misunderstandings, and interacting more naturally with native speakers, cultural awareness improves communication. It improves cross-cultural communication, builds empathy and respect for different lifestyles, and offers a stronger bond with the language. In the end, incorporating cultural awareness into language instruction fosters global citizenship and enhances linguistic proficiency while increasing learners' adaptability and sensitivity to the challenges of a multicultural society. By taking a comprehensive approach, learning a language becomes more than just an academic endeavour; it becomes a means of fostering deeper comprehension and deep interpersonal relationships.

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"Theoretical Perspectives on Cultural Studies"

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Annotation

The text explores cultural linguistics and linguoculturology. Cultural linguistics is described as a multifaceted field that examines the interaction between culture and language. V.V. Vorobiev emphasizes its integrative nature, while V.A. Maslova regards it as a humanitarian discipline that links both material and spiritual elements of culture as expressed in language. Triantis identifies three research approaches: indigenous, cultural, and cross-cultural. The indigenous approach focuses on specific cultural meanings, the cultural approach employs ethnographic methods to understand behaviors within social contexts, and the cross-cultural approach compares universal concepts across different cultures, addressing challenges related to fairness and accuracy. Key concepts include "emits," which refer to unique cultural features, and "ethics," which denote universal factors. The text underscores the importance of understanding how culture influences qualitative research in the realm of cross-cultural communication.

Key words: Cultural Linguistics, Linguoculturology, Indigenous Approach, Cultural Cross-Cultural Approach, Approach Emics, Etics.

Аннотация

В этом тексте обсуждаются культурная лингвистика и лингвокультурология. Культурная лингвистика определяется как сложная область, изучающая взаимодействие культуры и языка. В.В. Воробьев подчеркивает ее синтетическую природу, в то время как В.А. Маслова рассматривает ее как гуманитарную дисциплину, связывающую материальные и духовные элементы культуры, обнаруживаемые в языке. Триандис выделяет три подхода к исследованию: коренной, культурный и кросс-культурный. Коренной подход рассматривает конкретные культурные значения, культурный подход использует этнографические методы для понимания поведения в социальных контекстах, а кросс-культурный подход сравнивает универсальные идеи в разных культурах, сталкиваясь с проблемами обеспечения справедливости и точности. Ключевые концепции включают "эмики" — уникальные культурные аспекты, и "этики" — универсальные факторы. Текст подчеркивает необходимость понимания того, как культура влияет на качественные исследования в кросс-культурной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: Культурная лингвистика, лингвокультурология, коренной подход, культурный подход, кросс-культурный подход, эмики, этики.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu matnda madaniy lingvistik va lingvokulturologiya muhokama qilinadi. Madaniy lingvistik madaniyat va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirni o'rganadigan murakkab soha sifatida ta'riflanadi. V.V. Vorobyev uning sintezlash tabiati haqida ta'kidlaydi, V.A. Maslova esa uni til orqali topilgan moddiy va ma'naviy madaniyat elementlarini bog'laydigan gumanitar fan sifatida ko'radi. Triandis uchta tadqiqot yondashuvini ajratib ko'rsatadi: mahalliy, madaniy va kross-madaniy. Mahalliy yondashuv aniq madaniy ma'nolarni, madaniy yondashuv esa ijtimoiy kontekstlarda xulq-atvorni tushunish uchun etnografik usullarni qo'llaydi, kross-madaniy yondashuv esa turli madaniyatlarda umumiy g'oyalarni taqqoslaydi va adolat va aniqlikni ta'minlashda qiyinchiliklarga duch keladi. Asosiy tushunchalar "emiklar" — noyob madaniy jihatlar va "etiklar" — universal omillardir. Matn madaniyatning kross-madaniy kommunikatsiyada sifatli tadqiqotlarga qanday ta'sir qilishini tushunish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy lingvistik, lingvokulturologiya, mahalliy yondashuv, madaniy yondashuv, kross-madaniy yondashuv, emiklar, etiklar.

Cultural studies is a multidisciplinary field that investigates the complex interplay between culture, language, and society. V.V. Vorobiev, in his monograph "Linguistics: Theory and Methods," defines cultural linguistics as a complex scientific discipline that synthesizes various approaches to explore the relationships and interactions between culture and language. This definition highlights the multifaceted nature of cultural linguistics, positioning it as a crucial area of inquiry within the broader field of cultural studies.

Linguoculturology

Talia suggests that linguoculturology, a subfield of cultural linguistics, focuses on communicative processes within the context of ethnic mentality. This perspective prioritizes understanding how cultural context influences communication, emphasizing essential concepts such as culture-specific units, cultural concepts, and the national worldview. These notions are vital for unpacking the layers of meaning embedded in language and communication practices across different cultures.

V.A. Maslova further elaborates on cultural linguistics, defining it as a branch of linguistics deeply rooted in cultural studies. She characterizes it as a humanitarian discipline that explores both the material and spiritual dimensions of culture, which are embodied in national languages and manifest through various linguistic processes. This perspective underscores the dynamic relationship between language and cultural identity, suggesting that language serves not only as a means of communication but also as a repository of cultural heritage and values.

The Role of Linguoculturology

Linguoculturology emerges as an anthropologically oriented discipline that synthesizes cultural and moral experiences, as well as ethnic mentality, represented in language through specific cultural components. Maslova describes this field as an integrative area of knowledge that encompasses research findings from cultural studies,

linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and cultural anthropology. This interdisciplinary approach allows for a richer understanding of how language and culture inform each other.

Research Approaches in Cultural Studies

Triandis (2000) identifies three primary research perspectives in the study of culture, particularly in relation to cross-cultural and intercultural communication: indigenous, cultural, and cross-cultural approaches.

Indigenous Approach

The indigenous approach centers on the meanings of concepts within a specific culture, examining how these meanings may vary across different demographic groups. This perspective aims to develop knowledge tailored to the particular cultural context without making broad generalizations that may not apply outside of that context. A significant challenge of the indigenous approach is the difficulty in avoiding the influence of pre-existing concepts, theories, and methodologies, which complicates the task of defining what constitutes "indigenous" (Adamopolous & Lonner, 2001).

Cultural Approach

The cultural approach employs ethnographic methods and may integrate traditional experimental techniques. This perspective emphasizes the meanings associated with constructs within a culture and seeks to enhance the understanding of individual behavior within sociocultural contexts. However, it faces challenges related to the lack of a universally accepted research methodology, which can hinder the comparability of findings across different studies (Adamopolous & Lonner, 2001).

Cross-Cultural Approach

In contrast, the cross-cultural approach collects data from two or more cultures, operating under the assumption that the constructs being studied are universal. This approach aims to deepen the understanding of cross-cultural validity and the generalizability of theories and constructs. However, it encounters significant challenges in demonstrating the equivalence of constructs and measures used across cultures, as well as minimizing biases that could jeopardize the validity of cross-cultural comparisons (Adamopolous & Lonner, 2001).

Emics and Etics in Cultural Research

A critical distinction in cultural studies is between emics and etics. Indigenous and cultural approaches focus on emics—unique cultural elements that are specific to particular cultural contexts—while the cross-cultural approach emphasizes etics—universal factors that transcend cultural boundaries. Emics aim to provide a nuanced understanding of local contexts, while etics seek to identify and analyze similarities and differences across cultures.

Conceptual Implications

In summary, emics represent the "native's point of view," focusing on culturally specific insights, whereas etics embody a "comparative cross-cultural perspective,"

emphasizing broad applicability. These constructs are pivotal in the study of culture and play a crucial role in shaping the methodologies employed in cultural research. Triandis' classification serves as a reminder of the enduring tension between cultural specificities and universal generalizations, which continues to challenge qualitative research methodologies, particularly in the realm of cross-cultural communication. Having explored the conceptualization of culture within studies of cross-cultural communication, it is essential to examine how culture manifests in qualitative research processes. Understanding the presence of culture in qualitative research not only enriches the analysis but also contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities of human communication across diverse cultural landscapes. This exploration underscores the need for researchers to remain vigilant about the cultural contexts in which they operate, ensuring that their methodologies are sensitive to the intricacies of cultural dynamics.

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Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida estetik va madaniy qadriyatlar orqali musiqa atamalarining shakllanishi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida estetik va madaniy qadriyatlari orqali musiqa atamalarining shakllanishi shu o'rinda musiqiy atamalar yoshlar ma'naviyati shakllanishdagi o'rni va ahamiyatini ham yoritib bergan. O'zbek tili shakllanishi va rivojlanishida musiqa terminlarining o'rni misollar orqali ochib berilgan. G'arb tilshunosligida musiqa terminlarining o'rganilishiga oid tadqiqotlar nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvokulturologiya, estetik tarbiya, termin, musiqa terminlari, terminologiya, madaniyat, integratsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается формирование музыкальных терминов в английском и узбекском языках через призму эстетических и культурных ценностей. Особое внимание уделяется роли и значению музыкальных терминов в формировании духовности молодежи. Также анализируется влияние музыкальных терминов на становление и развитие узбекского языка с приведением соответствующих примеров. Кроме того, теоретически рассматриваются исследования по изучению музыкальных терминов в западной лингвистике.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, эстетическое воспитание, мировое языкознание, музыкальные термины, терминология, культура, интеграция.

Abstract. This article explores the formation of musical terms in English and Uzbek languages through the lens of aesthetic and cultural values. It highlights the role and significance of musical terminology in shaping the spiritual development of youth. The article illustrates the influence of musical terms on the formation and evolution of the Uzbek language with relevant examples. Additionally, it provides a theoretical analysis of studies related to the exploration of musical terminology in Western linguistics.

Key words: linguoculturology, aesthetic education, term, musical terms, terminology, culture, integration.

Til – insonlar o'rtasida aloqa almashinuviga xizmat qiluvchi, umumiy jarayondir. Musiqa-his-tuyg'u va kechinmalar, fikr va tasavvurlarni musiqiy tovushlar izchilligi yoki majmuyi vositasida aks ettiruvchi san'at turi. Nutq, tovushli signal va boshqa tovushlar orqali ma'nolarning ifodalanish jarayoni singari ham muayyan ma'nolarni ohanglar vositasida ifodalash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan jarayonning bir qismi hisoblanadi. Jumladan, tovushlarning baland-pastligi, ingichka-yo'g'onligi, uzun-qisqaligi kuchliligi va boshqa vositalar yordamida insonning ichki holatini ifodalash imkoniyati jihatidan musiqa nutqqa (nutq intonatsiyasiga) o'xshashdir. Dunyoda har bir xalq o'z tiliga va madaniyatiga ega. Til va madaniyat o'zaro

chambarchas bog'liq tushunchalardir. Madaniyatning bir qismi sifatida musiqani olishimiz mumkin. Madaniyatning bir qismi sifatida esa musiqa til va uning birliklari bilan aloqaga kirishib, biri-birini to'ldirib boruvchi ma'lumot almashinish vositasi vazifasini bajarib kelmoqda. O'zbek tili va musiqasi ham asrlar davomida birbiriga ta'sir ko'rsatib, birida yuz bergan o'zgarishlar ikkinchisida namoyon bo'lib kelgan. So'z va musiqa o'zaro assotsiatsiyaga kirishib, xalq madaniyatini o'zida aks ettirishi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Bugungi kunda jahon tilshunosligida musiqa va til madaniy antropologiyaning bir qismi sifatida qaralmoqda. Natijada, antroposentrik paradigma negizida lingvokulturologiya alohida fan sifatida tilshunoslik tarkibidan ajralib chiqib, o'z tadqiqot obyektiga, maqsad va vazifalariga ega bo'lib bormoqda. Nazariy tilshunoslikning ajralmas bir qismi sifatida shakllanib, rivojlanish bosqichiga o'tgan bu fan bugungi kunda o'zbek madaniyatining o'zbek tilida aks etishi, ifodalanishi kabi mavzularni o'rganish obyekti sifatida olmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda tilshunoslikning terminologiya va lingvokulturologiya sohalari manbalaridan foydalangan holda o'zbek tili tarkibidagi musiqa terminlari tahlil etilgan. Har bir soha o'ziga xos shakllanish va rivojlanish bosqichlarini bosib o'tadi. Soha tili hisoblangan terminlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari hamda ularning paydo bo'lish bosqichlari haqida olib borilayotgan turli ilmiy tadqiqotlar ham bugungi kun siyosatining mahsuli desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Musiqa sohasi bugungi kunda ham ijtimoiy birlik, milliy g'urur, estetik tarbiya va yoshlar ongini yuksaltirish vositasi sifatida muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Musiqa expressivlik vazifasini o'taganiligi uchun butun bir odamzodni bir xil mavzu bilan toplash qobiliyatiga ega chunki har bir inson tili, dini, madaniyati boshqa bolishi mumkin lekin u chekayotgan azoblar, his-tuyg'ulari, sezimlari va kechinmalari bir xil. Tillar o'rtasidagi o'zaro integratsiya natijasida bir tilga oid element boshqa bir tilga ko'chib o'tib o'zlashadi. O'zlashish jarayoni tilning terminologik sathida ko'proq uchraydi. Bir tildan ikkinchi tilga o'zlashgan termin dastlab adabiy til sathiga joylashib, keyinchalik o'ziga yangi hosila ma'nolarni yuklab so'zlashuv tiliga kirib boradi. Shu o'rinda aytib o'tish joizki: o'zbek tilidagi ko'plab terminlar ham o'zlashgan terminlar hisoblanadi.

Tilshunos L.V.Ivina termin haqida: "Termin – ilm-fanning inson faoliyati doirasi va bilish nazariyasi maxsus tarmoqlarining asosiy leksik birligi bo'lib, bir vaqtning o'zida obyekt va jarayonlarni nomlash va olamni anglash quroli hisoblanadi. O.S.Petrovskaya g'arb musiqa terminologiyasi tarkibidagi terminlarining 80% Italiya ijrochilik san'atining musiqa terminlari, 12% fransuz, 5% nemis, 2% ingliz, 1% lotin tilidan o'zlashgan terminlar tashkil qilishini aytib o'tadi. Bilamizki, XIX asrdan boshlab ushbu g'arb tarkibidagi musiqa terminlari bevosita va bilvosita o'zbek tili tarkibiga ham o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatgan. Shuningdek, O.Petrovskaya musiqiy terminlar arkibida grafik terminlarni alohida ajratish lozimligini ta'kidlab, ular ham ma'lum semantik xususiyatga ega ekanligini aytib o'tadi.

Xulosa:

Ushbu ikki til integratsiyasida musiqa terminlari faol bo'lib, o'zida madaniy birlik, til elementi va soha tili kabi xususiyatlari jamlashi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Musiqa terminlarining o'rganilishi, ularning shakllanish va rivojlanish bosqichlarini tadqiq etish orqali muayyan til tadrijini o'rganishga erishish mumkin.

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РОСТ ПОПУЛЯРНОСТИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ТУРЕЦКОГО ЯЗЫКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ПРИЧИНЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ

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Аннотация. В последние годы наблюдается значительное увеличение числа изучающих турецкий язык в Узбекистане. Это явление объясняется множеством факторов, которые можно разделить на культурные, экономические и социальные. Первая часть данной статьи посвящена анализу причин этого феномена, исследованию роли культурных, экономических и образовательных факторов, а также выявлению перспектив развития двусторонних языковых обменов.

Вторая же часть статьи рассматривает социальный аспект стремительного увеличения числа факультетов, предлагающих программы по изучению турецкого языка в университетах Узбекистана. А также исследует ведущие высшие учебные заведения, где преподаётся турецкий язык, анализируются используемые учебные материалы и методологии преподавания. Кроме того, исследуются внедрения турецкого языка на других факультетах, не связанных с лингвистикой, как второй иностранный язык.

Ключевые слова: Турецкий язык, методология преподавания, лингвистика.

Annotatsiya. So'nggi yillarda O'zbekistonda turk tilini o'rganayotganlar soni sezilarli darajada ortib bormoqda. Bu holat madaniy, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy omillar bilan izohlanadi. Ushbu maqolaning birinchi qismida mazkur hodisaning sabablari tahlil qilinadi, madaniy, iqtisodiy va ta'limiy omillarning roli o'rganiladi hamda ikki tomonlama til almashinuvining istiqbollari aniqlanadi.

Ikkinchi qism esa O'zbekiston universitetlarida turk tili o'rgatiladigan fakultetlar sonining keskin ko'payishi bilan bog'liq ijtimoiy jihatni ko'rib chiqadi. Shuningdek, turk tili o'qitilayotgan yetakchi oliy ta'lim muassasalari, foydalanilayotgan o'quv materiallari va dars berish metodologiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, lingvistika bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lmagan fakultetlarda ham turk tilining ikkinchi xorijiy til sifatida joriy etilishi o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turk tili, ta'lim metodikasi, oliy ta'lim, lingvistika, O'zbekiston, ikki tomonlama hamkorlik.

Abstract. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of people studying the Turkish language in Uzbekistan. This phenomenon can be attributed to various cultural, economic, and social factors. The first part of this article analyzes the reasons behind this trend, examines the roles of cultural, economic, and educational factors, and explores the prospects for bilateral language exchange. The second part of the article focuses on the social dimension of the sharp rise in the number of university faculties in Uzbekistan offering programs in Turkish language education. It investigates leading higher education institutions where Turkish is taught, analyzes the teaching materials and methodologies used, and studies the implementation of Turkish as a second foreign language in non-linguistic departments.

Keywords: Turkish language, teaching methodology, higher education, linguistics, Uzbekistan, bilateral cooperation.

Введение. Изучение иностранных языков в современном мире играет ключевую роль в процессе глобализации, международных экономических и культурных связей. Целью данной статьи является исследование причин роста популярности турецкого языка в Узбекистане, анализ программ обучения и выявление вызовов, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся и преподаватели. Методологически работа основывается на анализе существующей литературы, опросах учащихся и преподавателей, а также анализе программ обучения турецкому языку в Узбекистане.

Изучение турецкого языка в Узбекистане стало заметно популярным, и это явление неслучайно. Оно связано с комплексом факторов, охватывающих культурные, экономические и социальные аспекты, которые мы можем детально рассмотреть. Узбекистан и Турция делят богатое историческое наследие, восходящее к временам Великого шелкового пути и Османской империи. Эта общая история создает прочную основу для культурного обмена. Нынешний же период, это влияние “мягкой силы” Турции, то есть фильмы и сериалы, снимающиеся в Турции, завоевали огромную популярность, привнося элементы турецкой культуры в повседневную жизнь узбекистанцев. Благодаря им молодое поколение, а также и люди воспитанные в духе советского союза, проявляют живой интерес к изучению языка, чтобы лучше понимать и наслаждаться контентом. Узбекистан и Турция имеют общие исторические корни и культурные традиции что создает интерес к языку и культуре братского народа.

Популяризация турецкого языка в Узбекистане

Известно, что исторические и культурные связи между Турцией и

Узбекистаном способствуют увеличению интереса к турецкому языку. Общие элементы в истории, религии и традициях двух народов создают культурную привлекательность Турции для узбекских студентов. Телесериалы и фильмы, производимые в Турции, также играют значительную роль в создании популярности языка, так как они часто транслируются в Узбекистане и пользуются большим успехом. Безвизовая система на три месяца для граждан Узбекистана в Турцию, а также схожесть языка, оба языка из одной тюркской языковой семьи, тоже оказало огромную роль в сближение наций.

Не маловажный факт играет государственная поддержка и образовательные программы Турции под названием Стипендии Турции “Türkiye Bursları”, где Турция активно развивает образовательные программы для студентов из Узбекистана. Турецкие университеты предлагают стипендии для узбекских студентов, что мотивирует их изучать язык. Более того, в Узбекистане открываются турецкие культурные центры и школы, где преподают турецкий язык, такие как образовательные учреждения, спонсируемые разными фондом и другими коммерческими и государственными организациями.

Еще один важный аспект, это двусторонние политические отношения между Турцией и Узбекистаном, которые находятся на высоком уровне. Регулярные встречи на уровне глав государств, подписание соглашений и совместные инициативы в сфере образования и культуры способствуют популяризации турецкого языка как одного из стратегически важных направлений в изучении иностранных языков в Узбекистане.

Не секрет, что Турция является одним из крупнейших экономических партнёров Узбекистана, и это сотрудничество активно развивается. Турецкие компании активно инвестируют в узбекскую экономику, что создаёт спрос на специалистов, владеющих турецким языком. Многие студенты видят в изучении языка возможность получения престижной работы в турецких компаниях или участия в совместных узбекско-турецких проектах.

Экономические связи между Узбекистаном и Турцией развиваются с каждым годом. Турция является одним из крупнейших инвесторов в узбекистанскую экономику, и это создает новые рабочие места и возможности для бизнеса. Знание турецкого языка становится критически важным навыком для тех, кто хочет работать в компаниях с турецким капиталом или заниматься бизнесом с партнерами из Турции. С усилением связей открываются новые возможности для работы и бизнеса, где знание турецкого языка становится важным конкурентным преимуществом.

Существует также заметный социальный компонент. Миграция в Турцию за рабочими местами стала распространенной практикой. Многие узбекистанцы стремятся улучшить свои жизненные условия, и знание языка помогает

адаптироваться в новой стране. К тому же, увеличивающееся количество смешанных браков между узбекистанцами и гражданами Турции создает еще одну волну интереса к изучению языка, поскольку семьи стремятся сохранить связь с культурой и языком обоих родителей. Миграция также играет свою роль. Многие узбекистанцы ищут работу в Турции, и знание языка упрощает этот процесс. Кроме того, увеличение числа смешанных браков и семейных связей с гражданами Турции создает дополнительный интерес к изучению языка.

Таким образом, сочетание культурных, экономических и социальных факторов делает изучение турецкого языка особенно актуальным в Узбекистане, открывая новые горизонты и создавая возможности для дальнейшего развития взаимосвязей между двумя странами. Также многие образовательные государственные и частные учреждения в Узбекистане начали предлагать курсы турецкого языка, что делает его доступным для широкого круга людей. Частные языковые школы, а также государственные программы и университетские факультеты активно развивают учебные материалы и методы преподавания, что позволяет углубить изучение языка и культуры.

Методология обучения турецкому языку в Узбекистане

Изучение турецкого языка представляет собой многогранный процесс, требующий применения разнообразных методических подходов. Основные аспекты методологии обучения включают коммуникативный подход, использование мультимедийных ресурсов, адаптацию культурного контекста и акцент на практическом применении языка. Для того чтобы эффективно преподавать Турецкий язык в Узбекистане, местные преподаватели учились у ведущих специалистов лингвистов, тюркологов и филологов из Турции, а также ежегодно стажировались в ведущих ВУЗах Турции. От этого они активно используют различные методики, направленные на повышение эффективности изучения языка. В целом, можно выделить два направления: использование классических турецких методик, разработанных в Турции, и адаптация этих методик с учётом особенностей узбекских студентов, а также создание собственных образовательных подходов.

Преподавание турецкого языка в вузах Узбекистана основывается на нескольких ключевых методологических подходах и учебных материалах.

Одним из ключевых аспектов турецких методик является контекстное обучение, когда студенты изучают язык через реальные сценарии, такие как покупки, путешествия, работа или социальные взаимодействия. Преподаватели организуют занятия в формате диалогов, ролевых игр, что стимулирует развитие устной речи и понимания на слух.

Следующий важный метод, это коммуникативный подход, который лежит в основе современных методик обучения всем языкам. Он акцентирует

внимание на развитии навыков общения, что позволяет студентам активно использовать язык в реальных ситуациях. Большинство университетов Узбекистана используют этот подход в преподавании турецкого языка, который акцентирует внимание на практическом использовании языка в реальных жизненных ситуациях. Этот метод включает активное использование аудио- и видеоматериалов, участие студентов в диалогах и ролевых играх, что способствует быстрому развитию навыков общения. Кроме того, турецкие методы активно вовлекают студентов в использование мультимедийных материалов: аудио- и видеоматериалы, созданные для носителей языка, помогают студентам погружаться в реальную языковую среду.

Использование мультимедийных ресурсов, потому что современные технологии открывают новые горизонты для изучения языка. Мультимедийные ресурсы, такие как видео, аудиоматериалы и интерактивные платформы, делают процесс обучения более увлекательным и разнообразным. Использование фильмов, сериалов и песен на турецком языке позволяет студентам погружаться в языковую среду и улучшать навыки восприятия на слух. Так как все ВУЗы страны оснащены проекторами, телевизорами и другими техническими средствами, интерактивно проводить урок для преподавателей стало на много проще. Так же наличие доступа в интернет помогает активно следить за изменениями в сфере образования и моментально реагировать на новшества.

Использование онлайн-ресурсов и платформ для изучения турецкого языка, таких как Duolingo, Türkçe Öğreniyorum, и многих других сайтов, стало важной частью учебного процесса. Это позволяет студентам не только изучать язык в классе, но и продолжать обучение вне занятий. Некоторые университеты, активно внедряют цифровые учебные пособия и интерактивные упражнения в своих программах.

Индивидуализация обучения и индивидуальный подход к каждому студенту также играет ключевую роль в обучении. Учитывая различные стили обучения и уровни подготовки, преподаватели должны адаптировать методы и материалы под нужды каждого учащегося. Это включает дополнительные занятия для студентов с особыми потребностями или использование специализированных материалов для тех, кто изучает язык в профессиональных целях.

Адаптация культурного контекста от того, что изучение языка невозможно без понимания культурных аспектов. Программы обучения должны включать элементы турецкой культуры, истории и обычаев, а также обсуждение традиционных праздников, кулинарии и литературы, что помогает учащимся не только учить язык, но и понимать его контекст.

Практическое применение акцентируется на практическом применении

языка, который является важным компонентом эффективной методологии. Студенты имеют возможность использовать язык в реальных ситуациях, будь то в поездках, в общении с носителями языка или в написании деловой корреспонденции. Проекты, стажировки и обмены могут значительно повысить мотивацию и интерес учащихся.

По мимо признанных мировых методик, преподаватели турецкого языка в Узбекистане часто опираются на методы, которые используются в ведущих языковых центрах Турции, как мы знаем, практически в каждом большом ВУЗе Турции есть свой языковой центр по обучению иностранцев турецкому языку. Но самыми распространенными являются TÖMER (Турецкий и иностранный языковой центр при Анкарском университете) и языковая школа Yunus Emre. В этих школах, широко используются такие учебные пособия, как “Yeni Nitit”, “Yedi İklim” и “Yeni İstanbul”, в которых упор делается на коммуникативные подходы и развитие навыков общения в повседневных ситуациях, через четыре основных направления как чтение, сочинение, аудирование и темы для разговорной техники. Также учебники предоставляют комплексный материал, охватывающий грамматику, лексику, разговорную практику и аудирование. Преподаватели, прошедшие обучение в Турции или участвовавшие в программах академического обмена, применяют эти методики на своих занятиях.

Университеты, предлагающие программы по изучению турецкого языка в Узбекистане

1. Ташкентский государственный университет мировых языков является одним из ведущих университетов, где предлагаются специализированные программы по изучению турецкого языка. На базе кафедры восточных языков создано направление по турецкому языку и литературе, которое готовит будущих преподавателей, переводчиков и специалистов в сфере международных отношений. Университет также активно сотрудничает с турецкими вузами, такими как Анкарский университет и Университет Стамбула, что способствует обмену опытом и преподавательскими методиками.

2. Национальный университет Узбекистана также предлагает образовательные программы по турецкому языку на факультете филологии и языков. В последние годы университет укрепил связи с Турцией через программы академического обмена, что позволило преподавателям турецкого языка пройти стажировки в Турции и обновить свои методологические подходы. Программы включают как практическое владение языком, так и изучение турецкой культуры, истории и литературы.

3. Самаркандский государственный университет предлагает программу по турецкому языку на базе кафедры востоковедения. Программа охватывает

широкий спектр дисциплин, начиная от лингвистики и заканчивая культурными и социальными аспектами Турции. Университет также участвует в ряде проектов по совместному образовательному обмену с турецкими университетами.

4. Ташкентский Государственный Университет Востоковедения является одним из престижнейших вузов столицы с преподавателями по турецкому языку высшей квалификации. Преподаватели и студенты на регулярной основе ездят в Турцию на стажировки и конференции, где с гордостью представляют свой ВУЗ.

По мимо данных вузов, практический каждый уважающий себя как государственные, так и частные вуз имеет кафедру иностранных языков, где наравно с английским языком огромную роль играет турецкий язык. От этого из года в год большое число специалистов поступают на работу преподавателями турецкого языка и развивают эту отрасль.

Преподавание турецкого языка в университетах Узбекистана строится на совокупности турецких и местных методик, что позволяет эффективно обучать студентов, учитывая как особенности турецкого языка, так и культурно-языковой контекст Узбекистана. Использование таких подходов, как коммуникативные методы, грамматическая корреляция и интерактивное обучение, позволяет преподавателям добиваться значительных успехов в обучении студентов. Важность методики преподавания заключается в её способности адаптироваться к потребностям студентов, способствуя как быстрому освоению языка, так и развитию критически важных навыков межкультурной коммуникации.

Причины открытия новых факультетов и интеграции турецкого языка на других факультетах

По мимо филологических и переводческих факультетов, обучение турецкому языку активно практикуется и на других факультетах. Самыми распространенными по обучению турецкому языку являются политология, экономика, журналистика, военное дело и многие другие.

Экономическое сотрудничество и спрос на специалистов. В условиях укрепления экономических отношений между Турцией и Узбекистаном возрос спрос на специалистов, владеющих турецким языком, не только в сфере лингвистики, но и в таких отраслях, как бизнес, международные отношения, инженерия и туризм. Это привело к открытию новых факультетов, где обучение турецкому языку является неотъемлемой частью подготовки будущих специалистов. Например, на факультетах международных отношений и экономики НУУз, ТашГУВ, Дипломатия и УЗЖОКУ введены курсы турецкого языка как обязательные.

Политическая поддержка и академические обмены. Турецкое правительство активно поддерживает развитие образовательных программ в

Узбекистане. Программы, спонсируемые стипендиальные программы *Türk İşbirliği ve Koordinasyon Ajansı Başkanlığı* (ТІКА) (Турецкое Агентство по Сотрудничеству и Организации) и *Yurtdışı Türkler ve Akraba Topluluklar Başkanlığı* (YTB) (Директорат по делам турок за границей и родственных общин), способствуют привлечению студентов к изучению турецкого языка. Многие узбекские студенты получают возможность обучаться в Турции по программам академического обмена, что также стимулирует открытие факультетов, где турецкий язык является ключевым.

Культурная дипломатия и образовательная интеграция. Турция активно развивает культурную дипломатию в Центральной Азии, в том числе через создание турецких культурных центров и библиотек в узбекских университетах. Это способствует популяризации турецкого языка среди студентов и академического сообщества, что в свою очередь ведёт к открытию новых программ, не только филологических, но и в таких областях, как менеджмент, маркетинг и политология.

Преподавание турецкого языка в Узбекистане: адаптация образовательных подходов

Адаптация турецких методик для узбекских студентов

Преподаватели в Узбекистане часто сталкиваются с вызовами, связанными с культурными и языковыми различиями между студентами и носителями турецкого языка. Например, узбекский и турецкий языки принадлежат к одной тюркской языковой группе, что даёт определённые преимущества для студентов, но также вызывает сложности при изучении отдельных грамматических структур, которые в обоих языках могут различаться.

Некоторые преподаватели разрабатывают инновационные методики, основанные на их личном опыте и особенностях образовательной среды Узбекистана. Эти подходы включают интеграцию национальных особенностей учебного процесса, таких как активное использование языковых игр, групповых дискуссий и проектных заданий, направленных на создание междисциплинарных связей. Примером может служить грамматическая корреляция, когда преподаватели специально выделяют сходства и различия между турецким и узбекским языками, что помогает студентам быстрее усваивать материал. Такой подход включает в себя составление двуязычных текстов и учебных материалов, которые одновременно фокусируются на различиях и общих моментах между языками, что облегчает понимание сложных грамматических конструкций.

Также преподаватели активно работают над созданием контекстуальных упражнений, учитывающих узбекский культурный и социальный контекст. Например, многие темы занятий, касающиеся жизни в Турции, адаптируются

под реалии жизни в Узбекистане, что позволяет студентам чувствовать связь между изучаемым материалом и их личным опытом.

Заключение .Турецкий язык в Узбекистане приобретает всё большую популярность благодаря сочетанию экономических, культурных и политических факторов. Важно отметить, что данная тенденция является результатом как растущего сотрудничества между двумя странами, так и интереса узбекской молодежи к турецкой культуре и экономическим возможностям. Для дальнейшего развития необходимо уделить внимание улучшению качества преподавания, разработке новых учебных материалов и расширению образовательных программ, чтобы удовлетворить растущий спрос на изучение турецкого языка.

Однако, перспективы для изучения турецкого языка в Узбекистане остаются позитивными. С увеличением числа образовательных программ и укреплением экономических связей между двумя странами, можно ожидать дальнейшего роста интереса к языку. Введение современных технологий в образовательный процесс, развитие программ по обмену и стажировке также будут способствовать развитию этой тенденции.

Расширение программ по изучению турецкого языка в университетах Узбекистана связано с рядом факторов, среди которых ведущую роль играют экономическое сотрудничество, культурная дипломатия и поддержка образовательных обменов. Введение курсов турецкого языка на различных факультетах показывает, что данный язык становится неотъемлемой частью подготовки специалистов в условиях растущего турецко-узбекского сотрудничества.

Таким образом, популярность изучения турецкого языка в Узбекистане объясняется множеством взаимосвязанных факторов. Культурные, экономические и социальные аспекты не только способствуют интересу к языку, но и открывают новые горизонты для развития межкультурных связей и возможностей для молодежи. Этот процесс, безусловно, будет продолжаться, создавая прочные связи между двумя странами.

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ANALYSIS OF MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the methods of teaching a foreign language, pedagogical issues, the analysis of the educational process and includes a number of answers and solutions.

Keywords: Cabinet decision, educational process, projector, group lessons.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены методика обучения иностранному языку, педагогические вопросы, дан анализ учебного процесса и дан ряд ответов и решений.

Ключевые слова: постановление кабинета министров, учебный процесс, проектор, групповые занятия.

Annotatsiya: Chet tilini o'qitish metodikasi, pedagogik savollar ko'rib chiqiladi, o'quv jarayoni tahlil qilinadi va bir qator javoblar va yechimlar beriladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, o'quv jarayoni, proektor, guruh mashg'ulotlari.

Today, in our developing independent Uzbekistan, development is accelerating in all areas. In particular, great attention is paid to the education of young people. Resolution 610 of the Cabinet of Ministers focuses on teaching foreign languages to young people. In the current era of globalization, the emphasis on language is also very high in developing countries. The science of a foreign language is divided into four

parts (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which is given a separate concept and skills. Educational technology is the correct and effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness and quality of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technological tools is at hand in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking).

will come. For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to perform this process without a computer, audio players. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the student is required to pay attention to the pronunciation of the speaker, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. It is one of the most effective ways to teach and learn a foreign language using modern technology. In this process, including:

- When using computers, the reader can watch videos in a foreign language on a projector or electronic board
- see and hear performances, dialogues, movies or English-language shows possible;
- organization of groups on different topics;
- sing karaoke songs and play monologues in the direction of the student's interest.

The use of these methods makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective.

In the process of globalization, it is hard to imagine our lives without the internet. It is one of the most effective ways to use a language effectively in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. There will be an opportunity to communicate with foreign speakers through the Internet. Writing exercises can be improved by writing a letter via e-mail. The most important issue is the introduction of modern communication technologies in the educational process, their targeted and correct, effective use, through which the student's interest in a foreign language, increasing the effectiveness of teaching. This will create opportunities and increase the demand for innovative technologies in education. Today, there are several different methods of innovative learning technologies. If they use a wide range of topics in the classroom, the effectiveness of the lesson will be high and the interest of students in the lesson will increase. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education through the introduction of innovations in the educational process and their implementation.

The use of different roles, action games in the teaching of foreign language lessons, leads to an increase in interest in both the lesson and language learning. By working in pairs or small groups, it helps students to communicate with others. The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important tasks in the coverage of the topic, its delivery to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to illuminate a theme. When teaching a foreign language, it is advisable to explain new words, grammatical rules on the topic, using graphic organizers. These are also easier to remember if given through graphic organizers. The use of different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also highly effective.

Using tables in the learning process, students can follow a specific grammatical rule, such as composing sentences using tenses, placing new words. At a time when there is a high need to organize a foreign language, the effective use of modern information technology, innovative educational technologies in the educational process, presentation and implementation through presentations make this process effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies lies in their correct and effective use in the educational process.

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IQTISODIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASIDA IKKILAMCHI NOMINATSIYANING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. O'zbek tilining iqtisodiyot sohasi terminologiyasi tarkibida ham ikkilamchi nominatsiyalar – metafora, metonimiya, vazifadoshlik asosida bir qator terminlar hosil qilingan bo'lib, ularning paydo bo'lish xususiyatlarini aniqlash milliy tilshunosligimizning dolzarb masalalari hisoblanadi. Quyida shu haqida qisqacha to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tilshunoslik, terminologiya, tadqiqot, nominatsiya, metafora.

Abstract. In the terminology of the economic sphere of the Uzbek language, a number of terms have been formed on the basis of secondary nominations - metaphor, metonymy, and functional similarity, and determining the features of their emergence is a pressing issue for our national linguistics. This is briefly discussed below.

Keywords. Linguistics, terminology, research, nomination, metaphor.

Аннотация. В экономической терминологии узбекского языка ряд терминов образовался на основе вторичных номинаций – метафоры, метонимии, функционального сходства, и определение особенностей их возникновения является актуальной проблемой для нашего отечественного языкознания. Это кратко обсуждается ниже.

Ключевые слова. Лингвистика, терминология, исследование, номинация, метафора.

Ma'lumki, *nominatsiya* kelib chiqishi lotin tiliga doir so'z bo'lib, "nominatio" birligi "nomlash, nom qo'yish, atash" ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Tilshunoslikda *nominatsiya* termini nomlash xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan, ya'ni nolisoniy borliq unsurlariga nom berish va ularni ajratib ko'rsatish, ular haqida tegishli tushunchalarni shakllantirish uchun xizmat qiladigan yangi tushunchalarni hosil qilishning alohida usuli sifatida tan olinadi. Nominatsiya jarayonidan o'tgan, shunday jarayonning natijasi hisoblangan til birligi ham ayni shu termin orqali ifodalanadi. Ayrim olimlar *nominatsiya* terminini tilshunoslikning nomlash jarayonlari tarkibini o'rganuvchi bo'limini bildirish uchun ham qo'llaydilar²⁹.

Akademik A.Hojiyev *nominatsiya*ni til hodisasi sifatida quyidagicha ta'riflaydi: "Nominatsiya. (*lot.* *nomination* – atash, nom qo'yish). Tilda nomlash vazifasini bajaruvchi birliklarni (so'z, so'z birikmasi kabilarni) hosil qilish"³⁰. Ko'rinib turibdiki, nomlash vazifasini bajaradigan birliklar qatoriga so'z bilan birga so'z birikmasi ham kiritilmoqda.

Zahmatkash terminshunos A. Madvaliev *nominatsiya* jarayonida 3 jihat farqlanishini shunday ta'riflaydi: nomlanuvchi obyekt, nomlovchi sub'ekt, tanlab olinadigan til unsurlari. Alohida tushuncha, predmet, belgi ("go'zallik", "kitob", "aytmoq", "yashil"), muayyan belgilari bo'lgan predmet ("yashil daraxt") yoki butun bir voqea-hodisa ("Bahor!", "Qushlar uchdi") kabilar *nominatsiya* jarayonining obyekti bo'lishi mumkin³¹.

Endi tilshunoslar ko'p murojaat qiladigan O.S. Axmanovanning "Lingvistik terminlar lug'ati"da *nominatsiya* hodisasi qanday talqin qilinganligiga diqqat qaratamiz: "Nominatsiya. *angl.* *nomination*. 1. So'zning nomlash funksiyasi yoki tomoni, muayyan nutqiy vaziyat yoki kontekstda qo'llanadigan so'zning semantik aspekti. 2. (atash). Muayyan referenti bor so'zni muayyan jarayonda qo'llanishini nomlash. 3. Aynan nom berish funksiyasi"³².

Ma'lum bo'lmoqdaki, O.S. Axmanovanning lug'atida *nominatsiya* tilshunoslik termini sifatida ikki ma'noli istiloh shaklida izohlangan. Yuqorida keltirilgan

²⁹ Номинация / Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 6-жилд. – Тошкент: "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2003. – Б. 383.

³⁰ Хожиев А. Тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати. – Тошкент: "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2002. – Б. 70.

³¹ Qarang: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 6-жилд. – Тошкент: "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2003. – Б. 383.

³² Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. – М., 1969. – Б. 270.

izohlardan esa nominatsiya biron-bir tushunchani yoki narsa-hodisani so'z yoki tenglashadigan til birligi yordamida atash, nomlash jarayoni nominatsiya ekanligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Demak, nomi yo'q narsaga yangi nom berish birlamchi nominatsiya ekan.

Endi rus tilshunosligidagi manbalarga murojaat qilamiz. Tilshunos V.N. Teliya tilda avval nomlangan ma'lum bir narsaning nomini boshqa narsani ham atashga ishlatish yoki ikkilamchi nominatsiya deydi³³. Tadqiqotchi Y.V. Xomsova ham ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning lingvistik tabiatini V.N. Teliyaga yaqinroq qilib izohlaydi: "Ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning paydo bo'lishi inson tafakkurining tabiati va o'ziga xos xususiyati, tafakkurining abstrakt fikrlash hamda umumlashtira olish xarakteri, obyektiv borliqning barcha unsurlari o'zaro aloqadorlikda, o'zaro bog'liqlikda aks ettira olishi bilan bog'liqdir. Tayyor nominativ birlikni u uchun yangi semantik funksiyada qo'llash, odatda, bu yangi ma'noning avvalgi ma'no bilan bog'liqligi, o'zaro ichki aloqasi borligi sababli yuz beradi³⁴.

V.N. Teliya mazkur hodisani "semantik derivatsiya" ham deb hisoblaydi va ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning asosiy ko'rinishlari sifatida metaforik, metonimik, funkcionimik ma'no ko'chishlarini qayd etadi, shu bilan birga, ma'no kengayishi va torayishi, ma'noning maxsuslashishi kabi semantik o'zgarishlarni keltirib o'tadi³⁵. A.A. Reformatskiy ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning metafora, metonimiya, sinekdoxa, funkcionimiya (vazifadoshlik) hodisalarini sanab o'tadi. Eng ko'p kuzatiladigan ma'no ko'chish turi sifatida rang, shakl, harakat o'xshashligiga ko'ra ma'no ko'chishini – metaforani ko'rsatadi³⁶.

Yuqoridagi izohlardan ma'lum bo'ladiki, ikkilamchi nominatsiya bir so'zni ikkinchi marta narsa-hodisa yoki harakat-holatni nomlashda qo'llash, eski nom bilan yangi narsani atash hisoblanar ekan.

Tilshunoslikda "ikkilamchi nominatsiya" hodisasi ham bo'lib, u olamdagi narsa-predmet, belgi-xususiyat, harakat-holat kabilarni anglab bo'lgach, ularga nom berish jarayoni hisoblanadi. Tilshunoslikning tarixiy-an'anaviy, sistem-struktur paradigmalarida leksikaning ajralmas qismi deb hisoblab kelinadigan mazkur hodisa terminologiyada ko'p uchraydi. O'zbek tilining yuridik, tibbiyot, matematika, astronomiya singari ilmiy sohalarda ko'plab kuzatiladigan ikkilamchi nominatsiya iqtisodiyot, botanika terminologiyasida ham mavjud. Ushbu fan sohalari tarkibida ikkilamchi nominatsiya asosida hosil qilingan terminlarning o'ziga xos tarkibi vujudga

³³ Qarang: Серебренников, Б.А. Языковая номинация (Виды наименований) / Б.А. Серебренников, А.А. Уфимцева. – М.: Наука, 1977. – С.129. – 357 с.

³⁴ Хомцова Е.В. Вторичная номинация и анализ переносных значений предметно-бытовой лексики русского языка // <https://elib.bsu.by/bitstream/123456789/209275/1>. – С. 2.

³⁵ Бу ҳақда қаранг: Серебренников, Б.А. Языковая номинация (Виды наименований) / Б.А. Серебренников, А.А. Уфимцева. – М. : Наука, 1977. – С.177.

³⁶ Реформатский, А.А. Введение в языковедение. – М.: Аспект-Пресс, 2010. – С. 82-83.

kelgan. Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, jahon tilshunosligida terminlarning ikkilamchi nominatsiyaga munosabati masalasi – terminlarning ikkilamchi nominatsiya asosida yasalishi muammosi tadqiq qilinayotgan bo'lsa ham o'zbek tilining terminologiyasidagi biz o'rganishni maqsad qilgan sohalar terminlarining ikkilamchi nominatsiyaga ko'ra hosil bo'lishi monografik planda tahlil qilinmagan. Quyida ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning nima ekani, bu hodisaning iqtisodiyot terminlariga munosabati – soha terminlarining yasalishida qanday ishtirok etgani masalasini ko'rib chiqamiz.

O'zbek tilshunosligidagi yuqorida keltirgan ayrim lug'atlarda ikkilamchi nominatsiya termini berilgan bo'lsa ham, mazkur hodisani biroz boshqacharoq ma'noda mohiyati ko'rsatib berilgan: "Nominatsiyani vazifa va kelib chiqish jihatidan tekshirish uni azaliy, avvaldan mavjud bo'lgan (yoki hozirgi tilda tub deb qaraladigan) nominatsiya va yasama (ma'no va so'z yasalishiga ko'ra) nominatsiya deb ikkiga ajratishga asos beradi. Avvaldan mavjud bo'lgan yoki birlamchi nominatsiya jarayonlari – hozirgi tillarda juda kam uchraydigan hodisa: tilning nominativ boyligi, asosan, o'zlashmalar yoki ikkilamchi nominatsiya hisobiga – nominatsiya jarayonida oldindan mavjud bo'lgan birliklarning fonetik shaklidan yangi ifodalanayotgan narsaning nomi sifatida foydalanish hisobiga boyib bormoqda. Birlamchi nominatsiya natijalari muayyan til vakillari tomonidan azaliy, dastlabki nom tarzida idrok qilinadi (Masalan, *suv, tog', ichmoq, qora* kabi). Bunday nominatsiyalarning yasama ekanligi faqat etimologik yoki tarixiy tahlil orqaligina aniqlanishi mumkin. Ikkilamchi nominatsiya natijalari esa morfologik tarkibi yoki ma'nosiga ko'ra, yasama nom sifatida idrok qilinadi. Tilda tasviriy vositalar, perifraza va idiomalarning hosil bo'lishi ikkilamchi nominatsiyaning alohida holatidir"³⁷.

Ikkilamchi nominatsiya terminining semantikasida ma'lum bir til birligining ikkinchi marta biror ma'noning nomlovchisi bo'lib kelayotganligini ifodalash xususiyati bor. Mazkur termin ma'no ko'chirishining barcha usullari yordamida tildagi mavjud bo'lgan birlikni yana boshqa hodisaga nom qilib qo'yilishi hodisasini anglatadi. Bunda ikkilamchi so'zi keng ma'noli bo'lib, bitta so'z uch, to'rt, besh va undan ortiq narsa-predmet yoki hodisalarning nomiga aylansa jam ikkilamchi nominatsiya hisoblanaveradi.

O'zbek tilining iqtisodiyot sohasi terminosistemasida metafora usuli bilan termin hosil bo'lishi faol hodisa hisoblanganligi sababli metaforaning tabiati haqida to'xtalib o'tishimiz lozim. "Metafora. (*yun.* metaphora – ko'chirish). Bir predmetning nomini boshqa predmetga biror tomondan o'xshashligini e'tiborga olib ko'chirish. Metafora so'zning yangi ma'nolari hosil bo'lishida qatnashadigan omillardan biridir. Mas., qanot, kosa, arafa so'zlarining samolyot qanoti, tarvuzning kosasi, bayram

³⁷ Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 6-жилд. – Тошкент: "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2003. – Б. 384.

arafasi birikmalaridagi ma'nosi metafora asosida hosil bo'lgan"³⁸. Iqtisodiyot terminosistemasidagi ko'pgina terminlar shakl, belgi-xususiyat, harakat-holat, jarayon o'xshashligi asosida yasalganligi ma'lum bo'ldi.

Iqtisodiyotdagi *soliqdan qochish* terminining yasashida harakat o'xshashligi xizmat qilgan. Ushbu termin nisbatan yangi hosil qilingan bo'lgani sababli bu birlikda ma'noning ko'chmaligi juda aniq sezilib turadi. Jumladan, *soliqdan qochish* terminidagi *qochish* so'zida ham ko'chmalik xususiyati juda ochiq ifodalanadi. *Soliqdan qochish* terminining asosiy tushunchasini metafora yuzaga keltirgan. Jumladan, umumiste'moldagi *qochmoq* leksemasi ifodalaydigan ma'no iqtisodiyot terminiga harakat o'xshashligi asosida ko'chgan, "soliq to'lamay yurmoq" ma'nosi uchun birlashtiriladi: *Ushbu toifaga soliqlarni to'lashdan bosh tortadigan, soliqdan qochish sxemalaridan foydalanayotgan soliq to'lovchilar kiritiladi.* ("Soliq plus" gazetasidan)

Yuqoridagi tahlillarimiz o'zbek tili iqtisodiyot terminlarining ikkilamchi nominatsiya mahsuli sifatida yuzaga kelishida quyidagi xulosalarni chiqarishga imkon beradi: iqtisodiyot terminosistemasida ikkilamchi nominatsiya termin yasashining ko'p uchraydigan turi sanaladi; iqtisodiyot terminosistemasining diaxron aspektida ham, sinxron aspektida ham ikkilamchi nominatsiya faol ishtirok qilgan; iqtisodiyot terminosistemasida ikkilamchi nominatsiya natijasi bo'lgan terminlar so'z va birikma terminlar hisoblanadi; birikma terminlarning asosan hokim qismida metaforik ma'no ko'chirilishi eng ko'p kuzatiladi; metonimiya asosidagi termin yasashi kam uchraydi; vazifadoshlik usulida termin hosil bo'lishi kammahsul; ikkilamchi nominatsiya bilan hosil qilingan iqtisodiyot terminlarida terminning ko'chmalik xususiyati termin yangi hosil qilinganda juda ochiq seziladi, sohaviy adabiyotlarda, ommaviy axborot vositalari tilida davomli qo'llana borishi bilan so'zning ko'chmalik xususiyati sezilmaydigan bo'lib qoladi; ikkilamchi nominatsiya mahsuli sanalgan aksariyat iqtisodiyot terminlaridagi metaforizatsiya bugungi kunga kelib sezilmaydigan bo'lib ketgan; ikkilamchi nominatsiyadan iqtisodiyot terminlarini yasash natijasida o'zbek tilining mazkur sohadagi ichki imkoniyatlari, o'zbekcha so'zlarning sohaviy nutqda rasman qo'llanishini kengaytirgan; ikkilamchi nominatsiya natijasi bo'lgan terminlarning yana bir muvaffaqiyatli tomoni shundaki, mazkur terminlarni tushunish bu terminlarning o'rniga chet tillardan o'zlashtiriladigan terminlarga qaraganda oson tushuniladigan bo'ladi; chet tillardan o'zlashtirilgan terminlarning keng aholi ommasi to'liq tushunmaganligi sababli ikkilamchi nominatsiya mahsuli bo'lgan termin-metaforalar terminologiya uchun juda zarur.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

³⁸ Ҳожиёв А. Тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати. – Тошкент: "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2002. – Б. 63.

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SHUKUR XOLMIRZAYEV ASARLARIDA DIALEKTIZMLARNING LINGVOPOETIKASI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Shukur Xolmirzayev ijodidagi dialektizmlarning lingvopoetik vazifasi yoritiladi. Adibning hikoyalarida uchraydigan shevaga oid birliklar obrazlar xarakterini ochishda, milliy kolorit yaratishda qanday xizmat qilishi tahlil qilinadi. Parchalar asosida dialektizmlarning funksional-estetik roli ko'rsatilib, ularning badiiy matndagi ifoda imkoniyatlari ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: dialektizm, sheva, lingvopoetika, milliy kolorit, badiiy til, Shukur Xolmirzayev, hikoya, obraz.

Abstract. This article highlights the linguopoetic function of dialectisms in the work of Shukur Kholmirezayev. It analyzes how dialectal units found in the writer's stories serve to reveal the character of images and create a national color. Based on the fragments, the functional-aesthetic role of dialectisms is shown and their expressive possibilities in the literary text are revealed.

Keywords: dialectism, dialect, linguopoetics, national color, artistic language, Shukur Kholmirezayev, story, image.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается лингвопоэтическая функция диалектизмов в творчестве Шукура Холмирзаева. В ходе анализа будет рассмотрено, как диалектные единицы, встречающиеся в рассказах писателя, способствуют раскрытию характеров персонажей и созданию национального колорита. На основе фрагментов показана функционально-эстетическая роль диалектизмов и раскрыты их выразительные возможности в художественном тексте.

Ключевые слова: диалектизм, наречие, лингвопоэтика, национальный колорит, художественный язык, Шукур Холмирзаев, рассказ, образ.

O'zbek adabiyotida dialektizmlardan foydalanish orqali milliy ruh, xalqona

tafakkur, obrazlar tabiiyligini yaratish an'anasi mavjud. Shukur Xolmirzayev ijodi ana shu an'ananing yorqin namunasi hisoblanadi. Uning hikoyalarida ishlatilgan dialektal birliklar asarning poetikasiga chuqur ma'no, obrazlarga esa tiriklik bag'ishlaydi. Bu birliklar voqelikni badiiy idrok qilishda bevosita xalq og'zaki nutqining poetik imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish zaruratidan kelib chiqadi. Badiiy asar — bu nafaqat g'oyaviy-estetik in'ikos, balki milliylik timsoli sifatida ham qabul qilinadi. Asarda ifoda etilgan til unsurlari, xususan, dialektal birliklar (dialektizmlar) muallif maqsadini yanada teranroq ochishga xizmat qiladi. Dialektizmlar badiiy matnning lingvopoetik qatlamini tashkil etgan holda, xalqning mentaliteti, dunyoqarashi, yashash tarzini hamda ruhiy holatini aks ettiradi. Bunday birliklarning xalq ongiga va qarashlariga ta'sir eta olishini yaxshi anglagan ijodkorlar o'z asarlarida sheva va lahjaga oid asarlarni qo'llaydiki, natijada bunday asarlarning xalq ichiga kirib borishi, uning osnon o'qilishini ta'minlaydi. Biz bunday holatning taniqli ijodkor, O'zbekiston xalq yozuvchisi, o'zbek hikoyachiligining darg'alaridan biri Shukur Xolmirzayev hikoyalarida yaqqol ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Shukur Xolmirzayev hikoyalarida dialektizmlar faqatgina stilistik vosita emas, balki personajning ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi, mentaliteti va muhitini aniqlovchi semantik yukga egadir. Ayniqsa, **“To'y”** hikoyasida uchraydigan quyidagi misol bunga dalildir:

*“E-e, men-ku senga aytdim-ku, u qiz bola emas, **boladayammas**. Yana kelib kelinlik qiladimi, debdi-da...” [1]*

Bu yerda **“boladayammas”** (ya'ni “bola ham emas” ma'nosidagi shevaga xos forma) dialektal birlik bo'lib, oddiygina holatga baho berishda obrazning mental olamidani darak beradi. Bu kabi iboralar matnga jon, milliylik va xalqona mazmun olib kiradi. Ijodkorning **“Qorako'z” hikoyasidagi dialektik tilda yozilgan o'rinlar juda ham ko'p bo'lib, bu orqali ijodkor asarning juda xalqchilligi, osnon o'qilishini ta'minlagan. Masalan, “Qorako'z” hikoyasida quyidagi so'zlashuv parchasida dialektizmlar estetik vosita sifatida qo'llangan:**

“Anavi bolani ko'rdingmi? Qanaqa qiyofa? Qaniya, bir ko'rchi, yurish-turishiga qara.” [2]

Bu yerda **“qanaqa”, “qaniya”** kabi so'zlar me'yoriy adabiy tildan chetga chiqadi, lekin ular obrazlar nutqiga tabiiylik, hayotiylik beradi. Aynan ana shu og'zaki tildan olingan birliklar badiiy matnni xalq ruhiga yaqinlashtiradi.

Shukur Xolmirzayev o'z hikoyalarida dialektizimlardan faqat soddalikni xalqonalikni ta'minlash uchun emas, balki bunday birliklardan poetik ruh berish uchun ham qo'llaydi. Xususan, Shukur Xolmirzayev asarlaridagi dialektal birliklar ko'p hollarda **kinoyaviy ma'no** yuklaydi. Bu esa lingvopoetik tahlilda muhim o'rin tutadi. Masalan, **“Qoplon izidan”** hikoyasida:

“Voy dod, bu bola yomon bo'libdi-ku, yomon...” [3]

So'zlovchi aynan **“yomon” so'zini ikki marta takrorlaydi.** Bu nafaqat

hissiyotni kuchaytirish, balki xalqona tilda qandaydir kinoya, salbiy baho va hayrat ifodasini ifodalash vositasidir. Dialektal shakllarning takrorlanishi badiiy matn poetikasini jonlantiradi. Dialektal birliklar Shukur Xolmirzayev ijodida badiiy nutqning dramatik dinamikasini yaratishda xizmat qiladi. Asarlardagi voqealarning hayotiyliigi, obrazlarning ichki olami aynan xalq tilining jonli qatlamlari hisobiga boyiydi. Dialektizmlarning o'z o'rnida qo'llanishi esa muallifning xalq ruhiyatini chuqur anglashini ko'rsatadi. **Lingvopoetik kuchning tabiiy manbaysifatida sheva va lahjalar ijodkor hikoyalarida aks etganini ko'rishimiz mumkin.** Dialektal birliklar Shukur Xolmirzayev asarlarida nafaqat obraz tilining ifoda vositasi, balki butun badiiy muhitni tashkil etuvchi estetik komponent sifatida xizmat qiladi. Adib o'z hikoyalarida xalq og'zaki nutqining tabiiyligi, emotsionalligi va obrazlilik orqali personajlar ruhiy olamini chuqur yoritishga erishadi. Aynan shevaga xos bo'lgan so'z va iboralar orqali yozuvchi o'z asarlarida tasviriy kuch, badiiy rang-baranglik va milliy koloritni uyg'unlashtiradi. Masalan, **“Tog' o'g'lonlari”** hikoyasida quyidagi iboraga e'tibor qaratamiz:

“E-he, bu bolalar qanaqa yuribdi, o'zi, itdan qo'rqmaydigan, odamdan orqilmaydigan bo'lib ketishgan-ku!” [6]

Bu parcha o'zbek tilining janubiy shevalariga xos ifodalar — “e-he”, “orqilmaydigan”, “bo'lib ketishgan-ku” kabi shakllarni o'z ichiga olgan. Bu shakllar orqali nafaqat gapiruvchining dialektal tilga mansubligi aniqlanadi, balki uning hissiy holati, bahosi, hayrat yoki g'azab holati ham aniq ifodalanadi. Adabiy tilda bu kabi emotsional yondashuvlarni yaratish uchun qo'shimcha vositalar talab qilinadi, holbuki, shevada bu tabiiy tarzda amalga oshadi.

Shevaning lingvopoetik imkoniyatlari ayniqsa qahramonlararo dialoglarda yaqqol ko'rinadi. **“Qorako'z”** hikoyasidan yana bir misol:

“O'shanda bilmadim-da, keyin ko'nglim sezdi. Ayol odam bunday bo'lsa, nima bo'ladi endi?!” [2]

Ushbu parchada **“bilmadim-da”, “bo'lsa, nima bo'ladi endi” kabi shakllar og'zaki nutq tabiatiga xos bo'lib, dramatik intensivlikni kuchaytiradi.** Bunday tildan foydalanish orqali yozuvchi sahna ritmini oshiradi, emotsional fonni kengaytiradi va o'quvchini bevosita voqeaga guvoh qiloladi. Bundan tashqari, dialektal birliklar orqali Shukur Xolmirzayev voqelikni realistik tasvirlaydi. Uning tasvir obyektlari — **tog' ahli, cho'ponlar, oddiy dehqonlar** — tabiiy ravishda o'z shevasida gapiradi. Bu xususiyatlarni buzmaslik, ularning tilini adabiy lashtirib yubormaslik yozuvchining asosiy badiiy tamoyillaridan biridir. Misol tariqasida **“Qoplon izidan”** hikoyasida aytilgan quyidagi jumlaning o'limi:

“Bolam, bu yerda qoplon yuradi, befarq yurmagan, yuragingni hovuchlab yur!” [3]

Bu ibora faqat mazmun jihatdan emas, balki ifoda shakli bilan ham kuchli ta'sir

ko'rsatadi. “*Yuragingni hovuchlab yur*” iborasi metaforik xarakter kasb etgan bo'lib, shu bilan birga xalqona tasviriy ifodaning yorqin namunasi. Bu yerda dialektik shakllar (masalan, “hovuchlab yur”) estetik ta'sir kuchini oshiradi. Shuningdek, adib sheva orqali obrazlarning ichki dunyosi va jamiyatdagi o'rni haqida ham signal beradi. Bu, ayniqsa, xalqning tiliga xos istehzoli, kinoyaviy, kinik ifodalar orqali yuzaga chiqadi. Yozuvchi uchun bu — obrazni psixologik chuqurlikda ko'rsatishning bir yo'lidir.

Demak, shevaga xos birliklar Shukur Xolmirzayev uchun oddiy til elementi emas, balki badiiy effektlar majmuasini yaratish vositasidir. Dialektal birliklar orqali voqelik va obrazlar bilan o'quvchi o'rtasida hissiy ko'prik o'rnatiladi. Ular xalq ruhiyatini nafaqat ifodalaydi, balki uni estetik darajada idrok ettiradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, Shukur Xolmirzayev asarlarida dialektal birliklarning qo'llanishi tasodifiy emas. Ular muallif tilining poetik kuchini oshiribgina qolmay, xalqona ifodaning obrazlar ruhiyatiga uyg'unligidan dalolat beradi. Dialektizmlar orqali matn tabiiylashadi, obrazlar tili hayotga yaqinlashadi. Natijada, o'quvchi nafaqat matnni o'qiydi, balki uni eshitadi, his qiladi.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada falsafada til va tafakkurning mazmun mohiyati, haqiqat haqidagi falsafiy mushohadalar tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, tilning jamiyatdagi o'rni, til, madaniyat va tafakkurning o'zaro aloqadorligini tadqiq qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: falsafa, til, tafakkur, jamiyat, haqiqat, tahlil, madaniyat.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются философские наблюдения о сущности языка и мышления, а также истины в философии. Также изучались роль языка в обществе и взаимосвязь между языком, культурой и мышлением.

Ключевые слова: философия, язык, мысль, общество, истина, анализ, культура.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes philosophical observations about the nature of language and thinking, as well as truth in philosophy. The role of language in society and the relationship between language, culture and thinking were also studied.

Key words: philosophy, language, thought, society, truth, analysis, culture.

Ma'lumki, til - ko'pchiligimiz kundalik hayotimizda u haqda chuqur tahlil qilmay doimiy foydalanadigan muloqot vositasidir. Biroq, bir lahza tahlil qilsak, tilning nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki fikrlarimiz, e'tiqodlarimiz va dunyoni anglashimizni shakllantiruvchi omil ekanligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Falsafada til uzoq vaqtdan beri muhim o'rin egallagan. Platondan to Vitgenshteyngacha va hozirgi kungacha ko'plab mutafakkirlar tilning qanday ishlashini, ma'noning mohiyatini va so'zlarning voqelik bilan qanday bog'lanishini tushunishga intilganlar. Ushbu esseda men til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi munosabat haqidagi fikrlarimni, hamda zamonaviy falsafa va tilshunoslikning bu aloqa haqida yangi tushunchalar berayotgani to'g'risida mulohazalarimni bayon etmoqchiman. Shuningdek, tilning haqiqatni qanday idrok etishimizga ta'siri va u fikrlashimizga qo'yadigan cheklovlar haqida ham fikr yuritaman.

Til haqida jiddiy fikr yuritgan dastlabki faylasuflardan biri Lyudvig Vitgenshteyn edi. U o'zining dastlabki "Mantiqiy-falsafiy traktat" (1922) [5] asarida tilni voqelikning ko'zguisiga o'xshatgan. Bu qarashga ko'ra, dunyo faktlardan tashkil topgan, gaplar esa o'sha faktlarning tasvirlaridir. Ammo keyinchalik Vitgenshteyn o'z fikrini o'zgartirdi. "Falsafiy tadqiqotlar" (1953) [6] asarida u ma'no faqatgina so'zlarni predmetlar bilan bog'lash masalasi emas, balki so'zlarning maxsus "til o'yinlari"da

qo'llanishiga bog'liq ekanligini ta'kidladi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, til bitta oddiy tizim emas, balki vaziyatga qarab turli xil amaliyotlardir. Bu g'oya falsafaning ko'plab sohalariga, ayniqsa kundalik hayotda ma'noning qanday ishlashini tushunishga katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Noam Xomskiy kabi zamonaviy tilshunoslar boshqacha nuqtai nazarga ega edilar. Xomskiy barcha insoniy tillar Universal grammatika deb atalgan chuqur tuzilishga ega ekanligini ta'kidlagan. Bu nazariyaga ko'ra, til o'rganish qobiliyati inson miyasiga tug'ma xos bo'lib, barcha tillar bir xil asosiy tuzilmani turlicha ifodalash usullaridir (Chomsky, 2006) [2]. Xomskiyning nazariyasi asosan biologiya va sintaksisga qaratilgan bo'lsa-da, u muhim falsafiy oqibatlariga ham ega. Bu nazariya tafakkurimizning qay darajada til ta'sirida shakllanishi va qanchalik qismi tildan oldin mavjud bo'lishi haqidagi savollarga olib keladi.

Aksincha, Benjamin Li Uorf kabi boshqa mutafakkirlar tilning fikrlashimizga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatishiga ishonishgan. Bu g'oya Sepir-Uorf gipotezasi deb nomlanadi. Ushbu nazariyaga ko'ra, turli tillarda so'zlashuvchilar dunyoni turlicha idrok etishlari mumkin, chunki ularning tillari voqelikni qanday ko'rishlarini shakllantiradi. Misol uchun, agar bir tilda qorni ifodalovchi ko'plab so'zlar mavjud bo'lsa, boshqasida esa faqat bitta so'z bo'lsa, so'zlashuvchilar qorni turlicha idrok etishlari mumkin. Garchi bu nazariyaning kuchli talqini bugungi kunda qabul qilinmasa-da, ko'plab tadqiqotlar uning kuchsizroq versiyasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Bu esa tilning tafakkurga ma'lum darajada ta'sir ko'rsatishini tasdiqlaydi (Boroditskiy, 2011) [1].

So'nggi paytlarda faylasuflar va kognitiv olimlar til, madaniyat va tafakkurning o'zaro aloqadorligini tadqiq etmoqdalar. Qiziqarli yo'nalishlardan biri "lingvistik nisbiylik" g'oyasi bo'lib, u tilning tuzilishi o'sha tilda so'zlashuvchilarning fikrlash tarziga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkinligini anglatadi. Misol uchun, ayrim tillarda "kecha" yoki "ertaga" kabi vaqtni ifodalovchi maxsus so'zlar mavjud emas. Bu tillarda so'zlashuvchilar vaqt haqida ingliz yoki boshqa G'arb tillarida so'zlashuvchi odamlarga qaraganda erkinroq yoki o'zgacha tarzda fikrlashlari mumkin. Shunday ekan, savol tug'iladi: til faqatgina fikrlarimizni ifodalash vositasimi yoki u fikrlarimizni shakllantirishda ham ishtirok etadimi?

Til falsafasidagi yana bir muammo haqiqat masalasidir. Aytganlarimiz rostligini qanday bilamiz? Alfred Tarskiy kabi ayrim faylasuflar haqiqatning rasmiy nazariyasini yaratishga urinib, gapning voqelikka mos kelishini haqiqat mezoniga aylantirmoqchi bo'lishgan (Tarskiy, 1944).[4] Biroq, his-tuyg'ular, qadriyatlar yoki siyosiy qarashlar singari mavhum yoki subyektiv mavzularga yuzlanganda, masala murakkablashadi. Masalan, kimdir "Ozodlik muhim" desa, bu fakt hisoblanadimi yoki shunchaki shaxsiy e'tiqodmi? Til siyosat va ommaviy axborot vositalarida katta kuchga ega bo'lib, ba'zan u haqiqatni yoritish o'rniga yashirish uchun qo'llaniladi. Shu bois Mishel Fuko kabi faylasuflar tilning hokimiyat bilan aloqasini o'rganishgan.

Fukoning (1972) [3] ta'kidlashicha, bilim va haqiqat betaraf emas, balki hokimiyatdagarlar manfaatlarini aks ettiruvchi diskurslar mahsuli hisoblanadi.

Ingliz tilini ona tili sifatida so'zlamaydigan inson sifatida shaxsiy tajribamdan kelib chiqib, ikkinchi tilni o'rganish fikrlash tarzini qanday o'zgartirgani haqida ko'p o'ylayman. Ba'zi fikrlarni ona tilimda ifodalash osonroq, boshqalari esa ingliz tilida tabiiyroq chiqadi. Ba'zan hatto qaysi tilda gapirayotganimga qarab, o'zimni boshqacha his qilayotganimni sezib qolaman. Bu holat meni til va tafakkur o'zaro chambarchas bog'liq degan qarashga qo'shilishga undaydi. Shuningdek, ba'zi inglizcha so'zlarning ona tilimda aynan muqobili yo'qligini ham payqadam. Bu esa har bir tilning o'ziga xos madaniy asosi va dunyoni idrok etish usuli borligini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, til falsafasi murakkab, ammo juda qiziqarli soha hisoblanadi. U bizga so'zlarni qanday qo'llashimiz, bir-birimizni qanday tushunishimiz va dunyoga qanday munosabatda bo'lishimiz haqida chuqurroq mulohaza yuritishga yordam beradi. Til shunchaki passiv vosita emas, balki fikrlarimiz, e'tiqodlarimiz va xatti-harakatlarimizni shakllantiruvchi faol kuchdir. Uni qanchalik ko'p o'rgansak, o'zimizni va yashaydigan jamiyatimizni shunchalik yaxshi anglaymiz. Talabalar sifatida, o'z tilimizdan foydalanishimiz haqida o'ylab ko'rishimiz va uning fikrlash hamda xulq-atvorimizga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini doimo yodda tutishimiz muhim, deb hisoblayman. Til qudratli kuchga ega, va bu qudrat bilan birga mas'uliyat ham keladi.

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A Comparative Analysis of the Phonetic and Orthographic Features of English and Uzbek Musical Terminology

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Abstract

This paper compares the phonetic and orthographic characteristics found in the musical vocabulary of English and Uzbek languages. It investigates how musical words are sounded and written in both languages, stressing the effects of their individual sound systems and writing customs. The paper looks at loanword adaptation, the depiction of comparable musical ideas using various phonetic and orthographic structures, and the issues caused by transliteration and translation. The research intends to offer insights into the connection between language and music across several cultural settings by means of a comparison of these linguistic features, hence supporting a better knowledge of musical vocabulary from a linguistic angle.

Keywords: English and Uzbek musical terms, comparative languages, transliteration, speech, writing systems, and the adaptation of loanwords are some of the things that this course covers.

Introduction

Musical terminology is studied not only in terms of meaning and origin but also in terms of phonetic (pronunciation) and orthographic (spelling) realization. A comparative study of these characteristics in English and Uzbek, two languages with different sound systems and writing norms, is the main emphasis of this paper. Effective communication, translation, and cross-cultural awareness in the domain of music depend on a grasp of these distinctions and commonalities. English, a Germanic language with a Latin-based alphabet, and Uzbek, a Turkic language with a changed Latin and historically Cyrillic script, provide an interesting case study for exploring the interaction between language and musical expression.

Methodology

A focused corpus of musical terminology was gathered from reliable English and Uzbek sources. This covered: Music encyclopedias and standard English dictionaries (e.g., The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians, Oxford English Dictionary). Dictionaries of English-Uzbek and Uzbek-English, as well as specialist glossaries of musical words in Uzbek (where applicable). Musical vocabulary found in academic papers, musical scores, and journalistic writing in both languages. Phonetic transcriptions for English words mostly relied on the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) as shown in reliable dictionaries and phonetics tools. Where differences occurred, the more frequent or standard pronunciations were recorded. Considering the

phonetic values of the letters in the present Latin script, phonetic transcriptions for Uzbek words were founded on the generally acknowledged pronunciation norms of modern Uzbek. Where dialectal or regional variances in pronunciation are known to occur for certain musical terminology, they were recorded for possible debate. A comparative study was done to find similarities and variations in the phonetic realisation of cognate terms—words having a same origin—and loanwords taken in by each language. This included looking at stress patterns, syllable structure, and vowel and consonant inventory. The musical terminology' regular spellings in both English and Uzbek (using the present Latin script) were documented. To grasp the history of its written form, historical variances in orthography—especially when phrases may have been once written in the Cyrillic script—were taken into account for Uzbek. A comparative study emphasizing the link between spelling and pronunciation in both languages, the representation of comparable sounds using distinct graphemes (letters or combinations of letters), and the orthographic adaption patterns seen in loanwords. Using a comparative linguistic method, this paper examined the phonetic and orthographic characteristics of musical vocabulary in English and Uzbek. The approach included the following main steps: Phonological Systems: A Short Comparison

Feature	English	Uzbek
Vowel inventory	12 pure vowels + diphthongs	6 vowel phonemes
Consonants	Rich in fricatives, clusters (e.g., /ʃ/, /θ/)	Simpler consonant clusters
Stress	Lexical stress (can change meaning)	Mostly predictable stress (often final syllable)
Loanword adaptation	Minimal changes	Phonological nativization common

Example:

- English: *symphony* /'sɪm.fə.ni/
- Uzbek: *simfoniya* [sim.fo.ni.ya] – vowel epenthesis is added to break up consonant clusters.

Orthographic Features and Issues Loanwords in Uzbek and English: Adaptation Musical words acquired from English and Uzbek both change their spelling to different degrees. Especially from Romance languages, English keeps the original spelling of loanwords. Uzbek usually alters the spelling more closely to its phonetic system, which might cause orthographic modifications making the source less instantly clear to a speaker of the source language. For example, a very straight phonetic and orthographic translation of the Russian word "симфония" (simfoniya) in Uzbek Latin

script is "simfoniya". To show the phonetic and orthographic variations, let us look at some instances of musical terminology in both languages:

Musical Term	English Phonetic Transcription (IPA Approximate)	English Orthography	Uzbek Phonetic Transcription (Approximate)	Uzbek Orthography (Latin)
Note	/noʊt/	note	[nɔta]	nota
Melody	/'mɛlədi/	melody	[mɛlodi'ja]	melodiya
Rhythm	/'rɪðəm/	rhythm	[ritm]	ritm
Symphony	/'sɪmfəni/	symphony	[sɪmfəni'ja]	simfoniya
Maqom	/'mɑ:kɑ:m/ (approximate)	maqam	[maqəm]	maqom
Usul	/'u:su:l/ (approximate)	usul	[usu:l]	usul

These instances show how different sounds and spellings reflect similar or identical musical ideas because of the unique phonetic and orthographic systems of English and Uzbek. Though the degree of orthographic adaptation may differ, loanwords—especially those of international origin—often experience phonetic adaptation in both languages. The variations in phonetic and orthographic characteristics create difficulties in the translation and transliteration of musical vocabulary between English and Uzbek:

Phonetic Approximation: Because each system has its own sounds, it can be hard to find exact phonetic matches between two languages when transliterating words. A lot of the time, transliterations use the best match they can find, which can mean that some sound details are lost. **Consistency in spelling:** For clarity and consistency, it is important to set uniform spelling rules for copied words. It's important to think carefully about whether to keep the original spelling (which is what most people do in English) or change it to fit the orthographic rules of the target language (which is what most people do with Uzbek phonetic adaptation). While this piece is mostly about phonetics and orthography, it's important to keep in mind that the cultural and historical background of musical terms can also make it harder to translate them in a way that is semantically equivalent. Even if two words look or sound the same, they might have different meanings or refer to slightly different singing practices. It is well known that English orthography is "non-phonemic," which means that writing does not always match speech. As an example, choir is pronounced /'kwaɪər/, while bass is pronounced /beɪs/ in music but is spelled like "bass" (the fish).

On the other hand, Uzbek spelling is based more on sound, especially in the Latin and Cyrillic systems: Most of the time, what is written is what is said. There are still some differences, though, mostly with loanwords.

Examples:

Term (English)	Uzbek Equivalent	Spelling in Uzbek	Phonetic Adaptation
Orchestra	Orkestr	orkestr / оркестр	Cluster simplified if needed
Melody	Navo	navo / наво	Semantic substitution, not transliteration
Note	Nota	nota / нота	Phonetic spelling adapted to Uzbek sounds
Jazz	Joz	joz / жоз	Spelled phonetically to match Uzbek phonology

Common Patterns of Adaptation in Uzbek. Uzbek musical terminology has been subjected to a process of adaptation that has been influenced by Russian, Arabic-Persian, and, to a greater extent, English sources. In order to accommodate Uzbek phonotactics (i.e., the permissible sound combinations), Uzbek speakers naturally adapt foreign terms. This is due to the disparities in phonological systems. The following are the most frequently observed strategies during the adaptation process. Several patterns are observed when English or Russian musical terms are borrowed into Uzbek: Epenthesis (Vowel Insertion) To disrupt consonant clusters: Piano → pianino (via Russian), drum → baraban (adapted from Russian). Final vowel addition to align with Uzbek word structure: Rock → rok → rok musiqa (compound to contextualize the meaning). Phoneme Substitution, Sounds that are absent from Uzbek are replaced: /θ/, as in theatre, frequently undergoes a transformation into /t/ or /s/. However, /ʃ/ and /ʒ/ from Russian are preserved (e.g., joz). Translation vs. Transliteration Certain terms are borrowed phonetically, while others are semantically translated: Melody → navo (semantic match), while Symphony → simfoniya (transliteration). Phonetic Adaptation: Uzbek phonetic principles are applied to the pronunciation of foreign musical terms, including vowel harmony tendencies, consonant substitutions, and a stress transfer to the final syllable. The concluding inflection in the Uzbek word "simfoniya" is derived from the Russian word "симфония" (simfoniya). The word "jazz" in English is pronounced with Uzbek consonant sounds. Morphological Adaptation: The integration of foreign musical terms into Uzbek grammar is achieved by utilizing Uzbek plural suffixes (-lar), case endings, and the formation of verbs with auxiliary verbs such as qilmoq (to do). "Nota" (derived from Latin) is rendered as "notalar" (notes). "Aranjirovka qilmoq" (to arrange - derived

from the Russian words "аранжировка" and "qilmoq"). Semantic Adaptation: The meaning of borrowed musical terms may be condensed, expanded, or adopt slightly different nuances in the Uzbek musical context. The term "klassik" (from the Russian/international language) encompasses both the Western classical music and the Uzbek classical maqom tradition.

Incorporation of Musical Elements from Other Cultures into Uzbek Music This reading emphasizes the musical material itself. Though having deep native origins, Uzbek music has also been affected by and incorporated aspects from various musical heritages over time. Interactions with adjacent civilizations along the Silk Road most certainly resulted in the acquisition and modification of certain melodic patterns, scales, or ornamentation techniques. Especially important is the impact of Persian and Tajik music, which share modal systems and melodic contours. **Rhythmic Influences:** Although Uzbek music has its own intricate rhythmic cycles (usul), interaction with other cultures may have affected or introduced certain rhythmic patterns or tools. **Instrumental Adoption and Adaptation:** Uzbek musical groups include instruments of both native provenance (such as the dutor, tanbur, sato, rubob, doira) and those taken and modified from other countries (such as the gijjak, which has Central Asian ancestors). The Uzbek musical aesthetic has absorbed the playing methods and functions of these instruments into the group. In some kinds of Uzbek popular and contemporary music, often mixed with traditional melodic and rhythmic structures, aspects of Western harmony (chords, chord progressions) have started to emerge with more interaction with Western musical traditions, especially during the Soviet era and in modern times. This is a continuous region of change. Although the maqom tradition has its own unique shapes (e.g., shashmaqom), modern genres might borrow or modify Western song structures, instrumental piece forms, or hybrid forms combining Eastern and Western components. **Phonetic and orthographic variations can lead to:** Pronunciation difficulties for Uzbek students of English (e.g., "rhythm" /'rɪðəm/), Spelling problems with English vocabulary in Uzbek literature, Difficulties in translation: deciding between a native equivalent and a loanword.

Conclusion

The phonetic and orthographic traits of English and Uzbek musical vocabulary show the unique linguistic qualities of both language. English, with its complicated vowel system and historically affected spelling, differs from Uzbek's more phonemic writing system and diverse set of defining sounds. Loanword adaptation and the portrayal of common musical ideas show how every language fits and incorporates musical terminology. Accurate communication, efficient translation, and a greater awareness of the linguistic variety inside the worldwide scene of music all depend on an understanding of these phonetic and orthographic distinctions. Further study might investigate the perceptual elements of these phonetic and orthographic differences and

their influence on the knowledge and learning of musical vocabulary across language boundaries.

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ДЕТСКИЕ ОБРАЗЫ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ Ч. ДИККЕНСА И Л. АНДРЕЕВА

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АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье рассматриваются различные подходы к изображению детей в произведениях Чарльза Диккенса и Леонида Андреева. Образ ребенка у этих авторов может быть воспринят как жертва жестоких социальных условий или как символ высших духовных ценностей, а также как опора для взрослых, утрачивающих эти ценности.

Ключевые слова: образ ребенка, социальная жертва, мир природы, духовная опора, высший суд, оптимизм, пессимизм, декаданс.

ANNOTATION: This article examines different approaches to the depiction of children in the works of Charles Dickens and Leonid Andreyev. The image of the child in these authors' works can be seen either as a victim of harsh social conditions or as a symbol of higher spiritual values, as well as a support for adults who have lost these values.

Keywords: image of the child, social victim, the world of nature, spiritual support, higher judge, optimism, pessimism, decadence.

Образ ребенка как центрального или важного героя начал появляться в европейской литературе в первой половине XIX века. Первыми писателями, которые придали детям особое идеологическое значение, были Чарльз Диккенс в Англии и Виктор Гюго во Франции. В русскую литературу образы детей пришли с произведениями Льва Толстого, такими как «Детство» и «Отрочество», а позже они ярко проявились в творчестве Федора Достоевского, Антона Чехова, Николая Гарина-Михайловского и других авторов. Леонид Андреев также не обошел тему детства стороной. Хотя в его творчестве существует всего несколько рассказов, посвященных детям, эти произведения представляют интерес для анализа и позволяют оценить многогранность подхода автора к данной теме. Оригинальность подхода Леонида Андреева к изображению ребенка раскрывает эволюцию литературной традиции в его произведениях по сравнению с тем, как эту тему обрабатывал Чарльз Диккенс [1, 103], которого, судя по его высказываниям и упоминаниям в фельетонах, Л. Андреев хорошо знал и высоко ценил [2,98].

Как известно, судьба и роль ребенка в современном обществе глубоко волновали Диккенса, который, пережив в детстве опыт долгой тюрьмы, тяжелого труда и голода, проникся этим в своих произведениях. Уже его первый

роман, в котором он отразил эти мрачные воспоминания, потряс читателей и стал причиной реформы закона о бедных, за которую долгое время боролись, но безуспешно. Однако задача Диккенса не ограничивалась лишь изображением жестокой эксплуатации беззащитных детей, брошенных на самое дно общества. Он стремился найти духовную опору для человека в этом жестоком и противоречивом мире, и образ ребенка стал для него важнейшим символом духовной чистоты, добра и внутренней силы. Новый приход в мир, дети хранили в себе уникальный духовный потенциал, который взрослые часто бессознательно растрчивали. Поэтому у Диккенса дети часто становились поддержкой и ориентиром для заплутавших взрослых.

Многие из тем, затронутых в произведениях Чарльза Диккенса о детях, также встречаются в рассказах Леонида Андреева. Как отмечают исследователи его творчества, такие как Е. Панкова, Л. Кен и Н. Борзова, Андреев, как и Диккенс, не писал произведений для детей; его рассказы о детях были направлены к взрослой аудитории[3, 150]. Детская проблематика в творчестве Андреева близка к Диккенсу, однако она наполнена индивидуальными особенностями, что придает произведениям Андреева уникальную атмосферу. Также можно отметить еще одну схожую черту — глубокую чувствительность обоих писателей к новым течениям в литературе своего времени. В позднем Диккенсе прослеживаются черты натурализма и символизма, а в творчестве Андреева уже заметно влияние импрессионизма, экспрессионизма и декаданса. Интересно, что влияние Диккенса особенно ощущается в тех рассказах Андреева, которые имеют наиболее пессимистичный характер. Это позволяет не только провести параллели между подходами двух авторов, но и проанализировать различия в их изображении детских образов.

Образ Саши в рассказе Леонида Андреева «Ангелочек» глубоко символичен и многослоен. Время действия — Рождество — навеивает ассоциации с «Рождественскими рассказами» Чарльза Диккенса, в которых звучат похожие мотивы возрождения и просветления души. Сюжет Андреева, несмотря на свою внешнюю простоту, полон скрытого трагизма. Одним-двумя яркими штрихами автор рисует судьбу тринадцатилетнего подростка, только что исключённого из гимназии. Его озлобленность, направленная против жестокой матери и лицемерных «благодетелей», когда-то устроивших его в учебное заведение, становится понятной лишь в конце, когда читатель узнаёт историю его отца. Эта история, напоминающая роман Ж.Ж. Руссо о страстной любви бедного учителя к богатой ученице, вероятно, известна и самому Саше. Поэтому именно он приносит своему несчастному и слабому отцу ангелочка с ёлки, ангела, за которого он умолял на коленях у благодетельницы. Отец верит, что это посланница его прошлого, и его вера подтверждается: ангел действительно

приносит радость. Отец и сын, счастливые и умиротворённые, засыпают, а ангел, повешенный на печке, тает — так же, как и их временное счастье. Внутренний смысл рассказа в том, что Саша, не осознавая этого, безнадежно ищет в мире, полном дисгармонии, справедливость, красоту и смысл. В Рождественскую ночь для него ангел становится воплощением этой красоты и добра, способной принести хоть малую радость и утешение его измученной душе, а также душе его несчастного отца. Однако радость в этом мире столь же мимолётна и хрупка, как восковой ангел — она исчезает так же быстро, как появляется. И в этом состоит важное отличие рассказа Андреева от «Рождественских рассказов» Диккенса. Если в рассказах Диккенса духи Рождества могут воскресить душу, исцелить её и изменить жизнь, то для Андреева ангелочек — это лишь обещание, которое так и остаётся невыполненным. В мире Андреева нет места для оптимизма: мироздание здесь наполнено трагизмом и пессимизмом, где даже самые светлые моменты быстро тают.

В начале статьи мы кратко перечислили основные задачи, которые решал в своих произведениях Ч. Диккенс, вводя в них образы детей. Те же задачи характерны и для детских образов Л. Андреева. Единственным исключением является отсутствие исследования становления личности, что не удивительно, поскольку жанр рассказа, которым пользуется Андреев, гораздо меньше по объёму, чем роман, которым пользуется Диккенс, и исследовать в рамках рассказа проблему становления личности практически невозможно. Можно упомянуть рассказ «Молодежь», но здесь речь идет не о становлении личности, а об осознании юношей своей моральной ошибки и плате за нее. Однако для него, как и для Ч. Диккенса, образ ребенка, даже страдающего и угнетенного, остается главной надеждой на духовное спасение и главной духовной опорой взрослых в этом непростом мире.

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ИСТОРИЯ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЭПИДЕЙКТИЧЕСКИХ РЕЧЕВЫХ ЖАНРОВ В МИРОВОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена анализу истории изучения эпидейктических речевых жанров в мировой лингвистике. Рассматриваются ключевые этапы развития эпидейктики, начиная с античных времён, когда эпидейктические жанры были основными элементами риторики, и до современности, включая влияние разных научных школ и культурных традиций. Особое внимание уделено изменениям в подходах к классификации этих жанров, а также их функциональным и структурным особенностям в разные исторические периоды. В работе также рассматриваются работы ведущих лингвистов, таких как А. И. Коровин, В. В. Виноградов, Ю. Д. Апресян, а также современные исследования, включая работы о влиянии эпидейктики на массовую коммуникацию и политику.

Ключевые слова: эпидейктика, речевые жанры, риторика, лингвистика, жанровая классификация, история лингвистики.

Abstract. The article analyzes the history of the study of epideictic speech genres in world linguistics. It examines the key stages in the development of epideictics, from ancient times when epideictic genres were central elements of rhetoric, to the present day, including the influence of various scientific schools and cultural traditions. Particular attention is given to changes in approaches to the classification of these genres, as well as their functional and structural characteristics throughout different historical periods. The work also explores the contributions of leading linguists such as A. I. Korovin, V. V. Vinogradov, and Yu. D. Апресян, as well as contemporary research on the influence of epideictic on mass communication and politics.

Keywords: epideictic, speech genres, rhetoric, linguistics, genre classification, history of linguistics.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola dunyo lingvistikasi tarixida epideyktik nutq janrlarini o'rganish tarixiga bag'ishlangan. Epideyktikaning rivojlanishining asosiy bosqichlari tahlil qilinadi, antik davrdan boshlab, epideyktik janrlar ritorikaning asosiy elementlaridan biri bo'lganidan tortib hozirgi zamonigacha. Maqolada shu janrlarni tasniflashdagi yondoshuvlarning o'zgarishi, shuningdek, tarixiy davrlar davomida ularning funksional va strukturaviy xususiyatlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada epideyktika sohasidagi eng mashhur olimlar: A. I. Коровин, В. В. Виноградов, Ю. Д. Апресян va boshqa zamonaviy tadqiqotchilar ishlariga alohida urg'u berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: epideyktika, nutq janrlari, ritorika, lingvistika, janr tasnifi, lingvistikaning tarixi.

История изучения эпидейктических жанров в мировой лингвистике представляет собой многослойный процесс, который включает в себя элементы не только лингвистики, но и философии, социологии, культурологии и истории. Эпидейктика как область риторики ориентирована на создание и анализ жанров,

цель которых — воздействовать на восприятие аудитории с помощью похвалы или осуждения. Эти жанры занимают особое место в теории коммуникации, поскольку они связаны с ключевыми ценностями общества и его моральными ориентирами.

С момента своего возникновения в античные времена эпидейктические жанры претерпели значительные изменения. Они играли центральную роль в риторике, использовавшейся для политической пропаганды, философских рассуждений и культурных дебатов. Основной задачей данного исследования является обзор эволюции эпидейктических жанров, начиная с их античного происхождения до современной лингвистической науки.

1. Античный период и формирование эпидейктических жанров

Эпидейктические жанры в античной Греции и Риме были связаны с риторикой и политической практикой. Одним из первых теоретиков эпидейктических жанров был Аристотель, который в своей работе «Риторика» представил эпидейктику как часть риторического искусства, фокусируясь на ее способностях воздействовать на аудиторию через положительное или отрицательное оценивание. Эти жанры были тесно связаны с ценностями гражданской жизни, а также с моральными нормами того времени.

Античные ораторы использовали эпидейктику для того, чтобы выразить общественные идеалы и нравственные оценки. Например, в речах по поводу похорон или государственных праздников акцент делался на важности добродетели, чести и социальной ответственности. Сочинение эпидейктических жанров стало важной частью образовательной системы, особенно в контексте обучения молодёжи искусству риторики.

2. Средневековье и Возрождение

В Средневековье эпидейктика была тесно связана с религиозной риторикой. Монахи и священнослужители использовали эпидейктические жанры для проповедей, выражающих моральные ценности христианства. Несмотря на то, что в этот период жанры были значительно ограничены религиозным контекстом, сам подход к изучению этих жанров продолжал развиваться, в том числе в работах таких теоретиков, как Августин Блаженный.

В период Ренессанса эпидейктика пережила новый подъем. Возвращение к античным источникам, изучение древнегреческой и римской литературы и философии открыло новые горизонты для теоретиков риторики. Так, работы Петрарки и другие гуманистические произведения значительно расширили представление о роли эпидейктических жанров в общественной жизни.

3. Современные подходы и анализ эпидейктики

XX век стал временем, когда эпидейктика начала восприниматься не только как часть риторики, но и как самостоятельный объект лингвистического

анализа. В условиях постструктурализма и дискурсивной теории эпидейктические жанры стали рассматриваться как сложные речевые конструкции, которые отражают не только ценности общества, но и изменяющиеся структуры власти, идеологии и социальных отношений.

К современным исследованиям в области эпидейктики можно отнести работы по дискурс-анализу, исследование жанров в контексте массовой коммуникации, а также анализ их роли в политической и социальной жизни. Эпидейктика в современной лингвистике продолжает занимать важное место в изучении публичных речей, медиа-коммуникаций и политической риторики.

Современные исследования, такие как работы **А. И. Коровина** (*Эпидейктические жанры в риторике и литературе*), **В. В. Виноградова** (*Теория речи и риторика*) и **Ю. Д. Апресяна** (*Языковая личность и эпидейктика*), значительно расширили понимание роли эпидейктики в лингвистическом контексте. **Н. Д. Артемов** в своей работе *Эпидейктика как средство воздействия на аудиторию* сосредотачивает внимание на роли этих жанров в современных медиа и политической риторике.

Вклад русских и узбекских учёных в изучение эпидейктических речевых жанров также значителен. Среди них можно выделить таких ученых, как **Ш. Абдурахмонова**, **Г. Мухаммадиев** и **Ш. Шукуров**, которые внесли важный вклад в анализ роли этих жанров в узбекской литературной и риторической традиции.

Итого, мы можем сказать, что эпидейктика прошла долгий путь эволюции, начиная с античного времени и до сегодняшнего дня, занимая важное место в риторике и лингвистике. Эпидейктические жанры остаются актуальными не только в контексте академической науки, но и в реальной политической и социальной жизни. Современные подходы к их изучению позволяют лучше понять, как риторика и жанровая теория развиваются в ответ на изменяющиеся общественные потребности и культурные тренды.

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TIL O‘QITISH METODIKASI VA PEDAGOGIKA

**LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND
PEDAGOGY**

**МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЯЗЫКОВ И
ПЕДАГОГИКА**

Understanding E-Learning and Blended Learning: Key Concepts and Implications for Practice

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Annotatsiya: Raqamli texnologiyalarning tez sur'atlarda rivojlanishi ta'lim va o'qitish tizimlarini sezilarli darajada o'zgartirdi hamda e-learning va blended learning kabi innovatsion modellarni yuzaga keltirdi. Ushbu maqola web-asosidagi treninglar (WBT), o'quv jarayonini boshqarish tizimlari (LMS), virtual sinflar va bilimlarni boshqarish bo'yicha asosiy atamalar, infratuzilma va strategiyalarni o'rganadi. Turli tushunchalar va sanoat tajribasiga tayangan holda, tadqiqot asosiy ta'riflarni aniqlashtirish hamda aralash o'qitish (blended learning) yechimlarini joriy etishda uchraydigan muammolar va afzalliklarni yoritishni maqsad qiladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, aralash o'qitish individuallashtirish va o'quv jarayonini yaxshilash imkoniyatlarini taqdim etsada, uni joriy etish uchun tashkilotning qat'iy yondashuvi, kuchli infratuzilma va doimiy professional muloqot zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: Aralash o'qitish, Elektron ta'lim, Web-asosidagi trening (WBT), O'quv jarayonini boshqarish tizimi (LMS), Virtual sinflar, SCORM, Bilimlarni boshqarish, O'quv portallari, O'quv texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: Бурное развитие цифровых технологий значительно преобразило системы образования и подготовки кадров, способствуя появлению инновационных моделей, таких как электронное обучение (e-learning) и смешанное обучение (blended learning). В статье рассматриваются основные термины, инфраструктура и стратегии, связанные с обучением на основе веб-технологий (WBT), системами управления обучением (LMS), виртуальными классами и управлением знаниями. Основываясь на различных концепциях и отраслевых практиках, исследование направлено на прояснение ключевых определений и освещение проблем и преимуществ внедрения смешанных образовательных решений. Полученные данные показывают, что несмотря на высокий потенциал персонализации и улучшения учебного процесса, внедрение смешанного обучения требует организационной вовлеченности, надежной инфраструктуры и постоянного профессионального диалога.

Ключевые слова: Смешанное обучение, Электронное обучение, Обучение на основе веб-технологий (WBT), Система управления обучением (LMS), Виртуальные классы, SCORM, Управление знаниями, Образовательные порталы, Образовательные технологии

Abstract. The rapid evolution of digital technologies has significantly transformed education and training systems, giving rise to innovative models such as e-learning and blended learning. This article explores core terminology, infrastructure, and strategies related to web-based training (WBT), learning management systems (LMS), virtual classrooms, and knowledge management. Drawing on a variety of concepts and industry practices, the study aims to clarify key definitions and highlight the challenges and benefits of implementing blended learning solutions. The findings suggest that while blended learning presents remarkable potential to personalize and enhance learning experiences, its adoption requires organizational commitment, robust infrastructure, and continuous professional dialogue.

Keywords: Blended Learning, E-learning, Web-based Training (WBT), Learning

Management System (LMS), Virtual Classrooms, SCORM, Knowledge Management, Learning Portals, Instructional Technology.

Introduction

The integration of technology in education has led to a fundamental rethinking of how knowledge is delivered and received. E-learning, defined by its use of web-based platforms to distribute instructional content, has become a cornerstone of modern education. However, as noted by both international researchers³⁹ and Uzbek scholars, the transition to technology-enhanced learning requires a shared understanding of new terminology and tools. The present study aims to explore the foundational concepts of e-learning and the emerging model of blended learning a pedagogical approach that combines the best features of digital and traditional methods.⁴⁰

This article synthesizes insights from international e-learning frameworks, such as SCORM and the IMS Global Learning Consortium, along with research from Uzbek linguists and educators who have analyzed the application of blended methodologies in national education systems. A comparative approach is used to analyze definitions, systems, and pedagogical implications in both global and Uzbek contexts.

1. Web-Based Training (WBT)

Web-Based Training involves delivering structured learning modules over the internet. It enables asynchronous and synchronous learning, including virtual classrooms. Uzbek researchers have examined the efficacy of WBT in improving student autonomy in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan.

2. Virtual Classrooms

Virtual classrooms simulate traditional instruction with real-time communication tools. This format supports collaboration through shared whiteboards, video conferencing, and live chats. Foreign literature and local analyses agree that virtual classrooms encourage active participation and peer-to-peer learning.⁴¹

3. Learning Management Systems (LMS)

LMS platforms are central to tracking learner progress and managing course content. Uzbek universities increasingly adopt LMSs like Moodle and Canvas, supported by government initiatives to digitize education (Ministry of Higher Education, Uzbekistan, 2021).⁴²

4. Learning Objects and Portals

Bite-sized content, or learning objects, are essential in keeping learners

³⁹ Garrison, D.R., & Anderson, T. (2003). *E-Learning in the 21st Century*. Routledge.

⁴⁰ Karimova, D., & Rasulov, N. (2021). Blended learning in Uzbek universities: Opportunities and challenges. *Uzbek Journal of Pedagogical Innovations*.

⁴¹ Nematova, D. R. (2020). Using microlearning and learning objects in language education. *Language Teaching Methodology Journal*, 7(1), 14–19.

⁴² Ministry of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2021). *Digital Transformation Roadmap in Higher Education Institutions*. Government Press.

engaged. These objects are modular and reusable. Uzbek educators advocate for their use in language teaching, where brief, targeted lessons help reinforce grammatical concepts.

5. SCORM and IMS Standards

Globally recognized standards like SCORM ensure that learning materials are interoperable and reusable. According to Brandon Hall Group, such models are key to scalable content delivery. Local adaptation of SCORM-based tools is ongoing in Uzbekistan's vocational training sector.⁴³

6. Knowledge Management

In both business and academia, knowledge management ensures that institutional memory and expertise are not lost. Manville & Foote argue that successful knowledge strategies must align with performance goals.⁴⁴ In Uzbekistan, digital archiving and faculty development programs support the capture of tacit knowledge.⁴⁵

7. Blended Learning

Blended learning combines e-learning elements with face-to-face instruction. It is particularly effective for language learning, where both digital immersion and real-time feedback are important. In Uzbekistan, blended learning models have been piloted in teacher training colleges, yielding positive outcomes by Rakhimova and Toirov.⁴⁶

The evidence points to blended learning as a powerful educational strategy that aligns with the diverse learning styles of modern students. However, as Uzbek educators have observed, awareness and infrastructure remain barriers. Foreign scholars emphasize the importance of learner autonomy, a concept that must be cultivated in education systems with more teacher-centered traditions.

Challenges include:

- **Terminology confusion**, which impedes communication between providers and learners;
- **Technological limitations**, especially in bandwidth-dependent tools like virtual classrooms;
- **Lack of strategic alignment**, particularly where educational goals are not clearly linked to performance outcomes.

Despite these barriers, blended learning remains promising. Its flexibility allows educators to design highly personalized and responsive learning paths. It also

⁴³ Kurbanov, S. B. (2023). SCORM-compliant LMS platforms in Uzbek vocational education: Opportunities and obstacles. *Journal of Vocational and Technical Education in Central Asia*, 6(1), 33–40.

⁴⁴ Manville, B., & Foote, N. (1996). Strategy as if knowledge mattered. *Fast Company*, (April Issue). <https://www.fastcompany.com/28121/strategy-if-knowledge-mattered>

⁴⁵ Islomova, Z. (2022). Knowledge management systems in teacher development in Uzbekistan. *Education and Knowledge Management*, 3(2), 11–17.

⁴⁶ Rakhimova, S., & Toirov, B. (2021). Implementing blended learning in teacher education programs in Uzbekistan. *Ministry of Public Education Research Bulletin*, 5(2), 18–25.

fosters a culture of continuous professional development, as emphasized by both Uzbek institutions and global initiatives like UNESCO's Future of Education framework

Conclusion

As both a concept and a practice, blended learning represents a paradigm shift in modern education. By incorporating both foreign and Uzbek linguistic and pedagogical insights, this article underscores the universal and local dimensions of digital transformation in education. Success lies not only in adopting new technologies but in fostering a learning culture that is collaborative, adaptive, and learner-centered. The future of education depends on our collective ability to navigate this blend with purpose and clarity.

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The Role of Contextual and Process-Based Approaches in Effective Vocabulary Teaching: Theoretical Insights and Practical Applications

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Annotation: This thesis explores the vital role of contextual and process-based approaches in vocabulary teaching. It discusses the theoretical foundations that support these methodologies and illustrates their practical applications in language classrooms. The study emphasizes how integrating these approaches enhances vocabulary acquisition by promoting meaningful interaction with language and repeated exposure to new words. The findings suggest that a balanced use of both approaches leads to more effective language learning outcomes.

Keywords: Vocabulary acquisition, contextual approach, process-based approach, language teaching, vocabulary learning strategies, communicative competence, lexical development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu bitiruv ishi lug'at o'qitishda kontekstual va jarayon asosidagi yondashuvlarning muhim rolini o'rganadi. Ishda ushbu metodologiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi nazariy asoslar tahlil qilinib, ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi ko'rsatib beriladi. Tadqiqot ushbu yondashuvlarni integratsiyalash orqali talabalarning lug'at boyligini oshirish, tilda mazmunli muloqotni rag'batlantirish va yangi so'zlarga qayta-qayta duch kelish imkoniyatini yaratish orqali ta'lim samaradorligi ortishini ta'kidlaydi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, har ikki yondashuvni muvozanatli qo'llash samarali til o'rganish natijalariga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Lug'at o'zlashtirish, kontekstual yondashuv, jarayon asosidagi yondashuv, til o'qitish, lug'atni o'rganish strategiyalari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, leksik rivojlanish.

Аннотация: Данная дипломная работа исследует важную роль контекстуального и процессуального подходов в обучении лексике. В ней рассматриваются теоретические основы, поддерживающие эти методики, и демонстрируется их практическое применение в языковом классе. Исследование подчеркивает, что интеграция этих подходов способствует более эффективному усвоению словарного запаса благодаря осмысленному взаимодействию с языком и многократному воздействию новых слов. Результаты показывают, что сбалансированное использование обоих подходов приводит к более успешному изучению языка.

Ключевые слова: Освоение словарного запаса, контекстуальный подход, процессуальный подход, преподавание языка, стратегии изучения лексики, коммуникативная компетенция, лексическое развитие.

Introduction

Vocabulary is considered the key to language learning and communication. Without a rich vocabulary, students encounter significant challenges in understanding and producing language effectively. Traditional methods of teaching vocabulary often focus on repetitive memorization of individual words that barely results in long-term retention or genuine understanding. Existing pedagogical practice emphasizes contextualization of the learning of words and process teaching, in perspective of viewing

acquisition of words as a dynamic long-term process. This thesis tries to examine the two approaches, combining theoretical with empirical practices in teaching, aimed at encouraging more effective word learning.

Theoretical Foundations of Vocabulary Teaching

The contextual approach to vocabulary teaching is grounded in the belief that learners acquire vocabulary more effectively when words are presented within meaningful and authentic contexts. This approach is supported by Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis, which argues that language acquisition occurs when learners are exposed to language input that is comprehensible and slightly beyond their current level ($i+1$). Context helps learners infer meaning from context clues, enhancing understanding and retention. The theory also draws on Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory, emphasizing the role of social interaction and communicative contexts in learning. In contrast, the process-based approach views vocabulary acquisition as a multi-stage cognitive process involving repeated exposure, active engagement, and meaningful use. This approach is inspired by cognitive psychology models such as the Depth of Processing framework, which highlights that deeper cognitive engagement with a word (e.g., through usage, association, and elaboration) improves memory retention. It also incorporates the principle of spaced repetition, which ensures that learners encounter vocabulary at strategically timed intervals to reinforce learning. Both approaches are compatible with the Constructivist learning theory, which proposes that learners build their knowledge actively through experience and reflection. The contextual approach provides the authentic experiences needed, while the process-based approach structures the ongoing practice necessary for vocabulary mastery.

Practical Applications in Vocabulary Teaching

In application, the contextual approach encourages the use of authentic materials and communicative activities which set vocabulary into contextualized environments. For example, language teachers can use newspaper titles, video recordings, or dialogue which constitute real language usage. Role-play, project work, and narratives enable learners to naturally and contextually interact with vocabulary, thus facilitating greater comprehension and retention. Process-based advocates frequent and varied practice opportunities. Teachers introduce new words and do so deliberately but also have students encounter new words repeatedly in different activities: reading, speech drills, writing activities, and vocabulary games. Didactic tools like semantic maps allow students to observe relationships between words, and spaced repetition software or schedules allow review of vocabulary at intervals. Combining these techniques might allow learners to learn vocabulary incidentally and deliberately. It encourages the development of communicative competence through the support of contextualized and well-rehearsed knowledge of vocabulary.

Conclusion

On the whole, effective vocabulary instruction juxtaposes the contextual and process-oriented methods. Theoretically, the two methods complement each other through the use of meaningful input with systematic practice. In practice, the integration yields an enriched learning environment in which vocabulary is placed in context and cycled through varied iterative practice. This balanced method optimizes learners' vocabulary uptake, contributing to the enhancement of their overall language proficiency and communicative ability

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ONA TILI O'QITISHNING O'ZIGA XOSLIKLARI

Ahmedova Hikmatxon Tursunovna

Qo'qon DU o'zbek tili va adabiyoti

kafedراسi dotsenti

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada ona tili ta'limining dolzarb muammolari bayon etilgan bo'lib, ulardan lug'atlar yaratish va ular bilan ishlash hamda o'quvchilar nutqini rivojlantirish masalalariga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Abstract. This article describes the current problems of native language education, focusing on the creation and work with dictionaries, as well as the development of students' speech.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются актуальные проблемы обучения родному языку, особое внимание уделяется созданию и работе со словарями, а также развитию речи учащихся.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quv lug'atlari, o'quvchilar nutqini rivojlantirish, o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirish, yozma nutqni o'stirish, savodxonlik.

Keywords: educational dictionaries, development of students' speech, increasing students' vocabulary, development of written speech, literacy.

Ключевые слова: учебные словари, развитие речи учащихся, расширение словарного запаса учащихся, развитие письменной речи, грамотность.

Jamiyat hayotidagi yangi tarixiy sharoit, zaruriyatlar yangi ma'naviy ehtiyojlarni va ularni ro'yobga chiqishi uchun kengroq imkoniyatlarni yuzaga keltirar ekan, bu o'z navbatida jamiyat taraqqiyoti, istiqbolining qanday yo'nalish va xarakter kasb etishi, qanday yakun topishi ham aynan ma'naviy ehtiyojlar dialektikasiga, jamiyatda ma'naviy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga bog'liqdir. Shu boisdan ham Prezident Sh.M.Mirziyoev - "Dunyo shiddat bilan o'zgarib, barqarorlik va xalqlarning mustahkam rivojlanishiga rahna soladigan turli yangi tahdid va xavflar paydo bo'layotgan bugungi kunda ma'naviyat va ma'rifatga, axloqiy tarbiya, yoshlarning bilim olish, kamolga etishga intilishiga e'tibor qaratish har qachongidan ham muhim"⁴⁷, ekanligini alohida ta'kidlab o'tadi. Insonning kamolotga yetishuvi hech qachon osongina amalga oshgan emas. Bu juda qiyin va uzun yo'ldir. Jamiyatning bir tekisdagi rivojlanish jarayonlarida ham bu vazifa oson bo'lgan emas. Bugungi globallashuv jarayonlari keng miqyos kasb etib borayotgan, bozor iqtisodiyotining o'ziga xos qonunlari va tamoyillari tobora jiddiyroq bo'y ko'rsatayotgan hozirgi zamonda esa bu masala yanada murakkablashadi. Bu tabiiy jarayondir. Shuning uchun ham ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonlari tashkil etishda zamonaviy yondashuvlarga ko'proq ehtiyoj sezilmoqda.

Bu ehtiyoj o'laroq, ta'lim jarayoniga interfaol metodlarning, zamonaviy

⁴⁷ Ш.Мирзиёев. Миллий тараққиёт йўлимизни қатъият билан давом эттириб, янги босқичга кўтарамиз.

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o'qitish texnologiyalarining olib kirilishi ayni muddao va bu ta'limdagi yutuqlardan hisoblanadi. Amalga oshirilgan ishlar tufayli ona tili ta'limida bir qator ijobiy natijalarga erishildi. Lekin hali bajarilishi lozim bo'lgan bir qator ishlar borki, ularni amalga oshirmay turib ona tili ta'limini sifat jihatdan yangi bosqichlarga olib chiqib bo'lmaydi.

Ona tili ta'limi oldidagi muammolardan biri o'quvchilarga mo'ljallangan o'quv lug'atlarini yaratishdir. Ma'lumki, ona tili dasturida ona tili ta'limi vositalari sifatida darsliklar, lug'atlar va albomlar ko'rsatilgan. Bu vositalardan biri bo'lgan darslik hanuzgacha asosiy o'rinda turibdi, ya'ni qolgan vositalar ta'lim jarayonidan o'rin olgani yo'q. Rivojlangan xorijiy davlatlarda ona tili o'qitishda lug'atlarning darslik bilan yonma-yon vosita sifatida qo'llanishi ko'pchilikka ma'lum. Masalan, ingliz, nemis va fransuz bolalarining ona tili darslarida foydalanishlari uchun ommaviy nashr etilgan 20 dan ortiq lug'atlar mavjudligi adabiyotlarda qayd etilgan⁴⁸. Shunday ekan, oldimizda turgan asosiy vazifalardan biri o'quvchilar uchun izohli, faol so'zlar, sinonimlar, omonimlar, antonimlar, iborlar, paronimlar, uyadosh so'zlar kabi o'nlab lug'atlarni zudlik bilan tuzishimiz va ularni ommaviy nashr etishimiz kerak. Bu lug'atlar albatta, maktab, akademik litsey, kasb-hunar kollejlari kutubxonasidan o'rin olishi hamda ularni kompyuter xotirasiga joylashtirish, internet saytlariga kiritish lozim. Shu lug'atlar yordamida amaliy ishlarga yanada kengroq o'rin berish, o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirish, ularni so'zlarning sehrli olamiga olib kirish, so'z sehriga oshufta qilish, ularning imloviy bilimlarini mustahkamlash, bolalarga ijodiy tafakkur ko'nikmalarini singdirish imkoniyatlari yuzaga keladi. Bunday lug'atlarni tuzish uchun lug'atshunos olimlar va metodist olimlar, ilg'or ona tili va adabiyot o'qituvchilari birlashishi lozim bo'ladi.

Ona tili o'qitishni yaxshilash yo'lida bajariladigan ishlardan yana biri o'quvchilar nutqini rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratishdir. Ona tili ta'limi oldidagi asosiy masalalardan biri ham o'quvchilarda ijodiy fikr mahsulini nutq sharotiga mos ravishda to'g'ri, ravon ifodalay olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdir. Bu maqsadga erishishda o'quvchilarda notqlikka havas uyg'otish, o'z fikrini chiroyli va aniq ifodalay olishga qiziqish uyg'otish, o'zining chiroyli nutqi bilan boshqalarda o'ziga nisbatan hurmat tuyg'usini uyg'otish mumkinligini singdirib borish yaxshi samara beradi deb o'ylaymiz. Buning uchun o'qituvchining o'zi chiroyli nutqqa ega bo'lishi va bu orqali o'quvchilarga namuna bo'lishi lozim bo'ladi. O'qituvchi bolalarga yozuvchi va shoirlar, aktyorlar, nutqidan namunalar eshittirishi va shu orqali o'quvchilarda notqlikka havas uyg'otishga harakat qilishi kerak. Shundan so'ng o'quvchilarga kichik-kichik mavzularda matn tuzish va uni ko'pchilik oldida ifodalay olish

⁴⁸ .H.Ne'matov, R. Sayfullayeva. Ona tili ta'limi muammolari. "O'zbek tili bo'yicha davlat ta'lim standartlarini joriy etish masalalari" Respubblika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari..Qo'qon 2003.

ko'nikmalarini shakllantirib borish zarur. Ona tili mashg'ulotlrida o'quvchilar navbati bilan shunday chiqishlarni amalga oshirib tursalar va bu ishlar o'qituvchi tomonidan rag'batlantirilib turilsa, o'ylaymizki, o'quvchilarning o'z nutqlariga bo'lgan e'tibori borgan sari ortib boradi. Har bir sinf bitiruvchilari o'quv yili oxirida shunday notiqlik chiqishlarini o'qituvchilar, ota-onalar va o'rtoqlari oldida amalga oshirishlari kerak. Bunday notiqlik chiqishlari o'quvchilarning ona tili fanidan olgan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarini baholovchi mezonlardan biriga aylanishi kerak. Shundagina o'qituvchi ham, o'quvchi ham nutq malakalarini ovstrishga jiddiy e'tibor bilan qaraydi.

Ona tili ta'limi oldidagi azaliy muammolardan biri savodxonlik bilan bog'liq. O'quvchilarimizning imloviy savodxonligi talab darajasida emasligi hech kimga sir emas. Albatta, buning bir qator obyektiv va subyektiv sabablari bor.

Ona tili darslari jarayonida imlo qoidalarini o'rgatib borishga yetarli e'tibor berilmayotganligi, ayrim fan o'qituvchilarining mahalliy sheva ta'siridan xalos bo'la olmayotganligi, turli reklama va afishalarda savodxonlik darajasining pastligi, savodsizlik bilan yozilayotgan SMSlarning mavjudligi, o'quvchilarning o'zida xatosiz yozishga ishtiyoqning yetarli emasligini savodxonlik darajasining quyi darajaga tushib qolganligiga sabab qilib ko'rsatishimiz mumkin. O'quvchilarda orfografik bilimlarni yaxshilash uchun birinchi galda ona tili mashg'ulotlarida lug'atlar bilan ishlash yo'llarini keng yo'lga qo'yish zarur, chunki o'quvchi lug'at bilan ishlash jarayonida so'zning yozilishiga e'tibor qaratadi. O'qituvchi vaqti-vaqti bilan o'quvchilarga reklama va afishalar bilan tanishib, ulardan xato yozilgan so'zlarni, noto'g'ri tuzilgan gaplarni aniqlab kelishni topshiriq qilib berishi va shunday ishni bajarib kelgan o'quvchilarni rag'batlantirib borishi kerak. Maktablarda vaqti-vaqti bilan savodxonlik bayramlarini o'tkazib turish ham orfografik bilimlarni yaxshilashga samarali ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Savodxonlik bayramida eng savodxon o'quvchilar aniqlanib rag'atlantirilishi, savodxonlik bilan yozilgan insho va bayonlar, tabrik matnlari, ona tili va boshqa fanlardan yuritilgan daftarlar namoyish qilinishi zarur. Bularning barchasi qolgan o'quvchilarda savodxonlikka ishtiyoq uygotadi. Kezi kelganda aytib o'tishni joiz deb bilamizki, savodxonlik bayramlarini ommaviy miqyosda o'tkazish lozim, ya'ni savodxonlik masalasiga keng jamoatchilik e'tiborini qaratish zarur. Barcha oliy o'quv yurtlarining talabalari, muassasa va korxonlarning xodimlari bu bayramda o'z diktantlari bilan qatnashishlari kerak. Yozdirilgan diktant natijalari xodimning maoshiga ta'sir o'tkazishi lozim. Shundagina savodxonlikka ehtiyoj tug'iladi.

Ona tili ta'limini sifat jihatdan ko'tarishning asosiy yo'llaridan biri bo'lajak o'zbek tili va adabiyoti o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashga eng muhim vazifa sifatida qarashdir. Ona tilidan DTS talablarini, dasrturda ko'zda tutilgan maqsadlarni amalga oshiruvchi asosiy shaxs ona tili o'qituvchisidir. Ona tili o'qituvchisining bilim darajasi past bo'lsa, u dars berayotgan sinf o'quvchilarining bilimi haqida so'z yuritib bo'lmaydi. Kadrlarni saralab ishga qabul qilish vaqti keldi, chunki kadrlarimiz miqdor

jihattan yetarli. Shundagina o'qituvchilar o'z ustida tinimsiz ishlaydi, oily ta'limda o'qiyotgan talaba yaxshiroq bilim olishga intiladi.

Ona tili ta'limining sifati boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarining bilim darajasiga uzviy bog'liq. Agar o'quvchi boshlang'ich ta'limdan chiroylli husnixat yozishni bilmasdan, yaxshi o'qish malakasini egallamasdan chiqadigan bo'lsa, ona tili o'qituvchisi ularni yozishga, o'qishga o'rgatadimi yoki datsur materiallarini ularga tushuntiradimi? Albatta, bu masalaga jiddiy e'tibor beradigan payt keldi. Buning uchun boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarini tayyorlash sifatini ham, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni o'qitish sifatini ham yuksak darajaga ko'tarish kerak. Shundagina ko'zlangan maqsadga erishish mumkin bo'ladi.

Shuningdek, bugungi kunda yangi bilimlar miqdori, hajmi tobora kengayib bormoqda. Axborotlar oqimining kuchayib borishi ham odatdagi holga aylanib qoldi. Ayni paytda ularni o'zlashtirish darajasi nisbatan orqada qolayotgani ham sir emas. Shuning uchun ham an'anaviy ta'lim usullari bilan birgalikda zamonaviy, yangi yondashuvlar ham o'qituvchi va murabbiylarni ko'proq qiziqirmoqda. Ayniqsa, o'quvchilarning bilimini chuqurlashtiradigan, bilimlarni o'zlashtirish jarayonini jadallashtirish va qiziqarli bo'lishiga imkon beradigan shakl va usullarning joriy etilishidan ular ko'proq manfaatdor bo'lib qolmoqda.

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Сравнительный анализ лексических изменений, вызванных цифровыми технологиями, в английском, русском и узбекском языках

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada raqamli texnologiyalar ta'sirida ingliz, rus va o'zbek tillaridagi leksik o'zgarishlar taqqosiy tahlil qilinadi. Axborot-kommunikatsiya vositalarining rivojlanishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan yangi so'zlar, terminlar, neologizmlar va ularning ijtimoiy-lingvistik xususiyatlari o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli til, leksik o'zgarish, neologizm, texnologik ta'sir, ingliz, rus, o'zbek tili.

Аннотация

В статье проводится сравнительный анализ лексических изменений, вызванных развитием цифровых технологий, в английском, русском и узбекском языках. Рассматриваются новые термины, заимствования, неологизмы и их влияние на структуру языка и общественное восприятие.

Ключевые слова: цифровой язык, лексические изменения, неологизмы, технологическое влияние, английский, русский, узбекский языки.

Abstract

This article provides a comparative analysis of lexical changes influenced by digital technologies in English, Russian, and Uzbek languages. It explores the emergence of new terms, borrowings, and neologisms, and examines their sociolinguistic implications in modern discourse.

Keywords: digital language, lexical change, neologism, technological influence, English, Russian, Uzbek.

1. Введение

С начала XXI века цифровые технологии прочно вошли в повседневную жизнь человека, радикально изменив способы коммуникации, восприятия информации и использования языка. Эти трансформации нашли отражение прежде всего в лексике, так как именно она наиболее чувствительна к новшествам. Новые реалии требуют новых слов: одни создаются заново, другие заимствуются, третьи — переосмысливаются. Языки, находясь в постоянном контакте друг с другом, влияют друг на друга и взаимно обогащаются.

Актуальность данной темы обусловлена тем, что в условиях глобализации и цифровизации лексика становится маркером не только языковых изменений, но и социокультурных процессов. Цель статьи — проследить, как английский, русский и узбекский языки реагируют на технологические нововведения, какие лексические изменения происходят в каждом из них, и как

эти изменения отражают общие и уникальные особенности соответствующих культур.

2. Теоретический обзор

Современная лингвистика рассматривает язык как живую систему, реагирующую на внешние изменения. Crystal (2006) утверждает, что интернет создаёт уникальную коммуникативную среду, в которой формируются новые языковые нормы. Baron (2008) вводит понятие "киберязыка", обозначая особенности языка в цифровом пространстве: сжатость, мультимодальность, эмодзификация, сленговость. Эти характеристики особенно ярко проявляются в социальных сетях и мессенджерах.

Английский язык, будучи глобальным языком цифровых технологий, выступает основным источником новых лексических единиц. Русский язык принимает как прямые заимствования, так и адаптированные формы, тогда как узбекский язык демонстрирует более осторожный подход, предпочитая кальки, локализацию и семантическое переосмысление.

3. Методология

В рамках исследования были отобраны 300 лексических единиц, появившихся или изменивших значение в результате цифровых технологий. Материал собирался из следующих источников:

- английский корпус COCA;
- Национальный корпус русского языка;
- uzbekcorpus.uz;
- Twitter, Telegram, YouTube, онлайн-форумы и СМИ.

Применялись методы лексико-семантического анализа, контент-анализа, сопоставительного описания и прагматической интерпретации.

4. Результаты и обсуждение

4.1 Лексика английского языка

В английском языке наблюдается активное образование неологизмов: как на основе словообразовательных моделей (например, binge-watch, unfriend), так и путём конденсации фраз (selfie, vlog, meme). Многие слова проникают в обыденную речь за счёт их распространения в цифровом пространстве.

Также развивается цифровой сленг: acronyms (LOL, BRB, FOMO), hybrid expressions (doomscrolling, ghosting), emoji-based phrases. Всё это демонстрирует не только технологический, но и когнитивный сдвиг в коммуникации.

4.2 Лексика русского языка

Русский язык в последние два десятилетия активно заимствует лексику из английского языка, особенно в сферах IT, социальных медиа и маркетинга: блог, хештег, лайкать, стримить. Наряду с этим формируются и собственные адаптации: кибербуллинг, фейк, скам.

Происходит словообразование на базе заимствованных корней: стримить — стример, лайк — лайкнуть, пост — постинг. Несмотря на протесты пуристов, новые слова входят в обиход, особенно в молодёжной среде и в неформальной речи.

4.3 Лексика узбекского языка

Узбекский язык демонстрирует более сдержанную реакцию. Многие термины заимствуются в транслитерационной форме (blogger, kompyuter, wi-fi), но наблюдается также тенденция к калькированию: "tarqatmoq" (share), "yuklab olmoq" (download), "qidiruv tizimi" (search engine).

Интересно, что в отличие от русского языка, узбекский часто стремится адаптировать иностранные слова к национальным нормам. Тем не менее, среди молодежи активно используются непереуведённые англицизмы, особенно в социальных сетях.

4.4 Общие и отличительные черты

Влияние цифровизации на лексику проявляется в:

- создании новых слов (неологизмов);
- заимствованиях из английского языка;
- изменении значений уже существующих слов;
- формировании цифрового жаргона.

Английский язык остаётся источником, русский — адаптивным посредником, а узбекский — отбирающим и локализующим.

5. Заключение

Результаты анализа показали, что цифровые технологии играют ключевую роль в трансформации лексики современных языков. В английском языке этот процесс характеризуется активным словотворчеством и распространением через глобальные платформы. Русский язык демонстрирует высокую степень заимствования и адаптации, формируя новые словоформы. Узбекский язык, несмотря на ограниченность ресурсов, развивает свои способы интеграции цифровой лексики, преимущественно через калькирование и контекстуализацию.

Необходимость стандартизации терминологии, разработка словарей новых слов, интеграция цифровых реалий в образовательный процесс — всё это открывает перспективы для дальнейших исследований. Изучение цифровых лексических изменений важно не только для лингвистов, но и для педагогов, переводчиков и разработчиков языковой политики в условиях информационного общества.

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Competitive Education System as the Foundation of the Country's Innovative Development

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Abstract. This article explores the issues of an innovative breakthrough in a country, which must possess a high-quality education system at all levels. A new approach to development planning is reflected in the adopted *Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan*[1], which represents an innovative reform program for the country's education system in the near future.

Keywords: education, reform, quality, innovation, ideas, program, science, technology, development.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mamlakatning innovatsion yutuqlarga erishish masalalari o'rganilgan bo'lib, buning uchun barcha bosqichlarda sifatli ta'lim tizimiga ega bo'lishi zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Rivojlanish rejalashtirish dasturiga yangicha yondashuv O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha qabul qilingan Harakatlar strategiyasida aks ettirilgan bo'lib[1], u yaqin istiqboldagi mamlakat ta'lim tizimi islohotlarining innovatsion dasturi hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, islohot, sifat, innovatsiya, g'oyalar, dastur, fan, texnologiya, rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В статье исследованы вопросы инновационного прорыва страны, которая должна иметь качественную систему образования на всех уровнях. Новый подход к программе развития планирования отображен в принятой Стратегии действий по дальнейшему развитию Республики Узбекистан, которая является инновационной программой реформ системы образования страны на ближайший период [1].

Ключевые слова: образование, реформа, качество, инновации, идеи, программа, наука, технология, развитие.

In the context of globalization and rapid changes in technological and economic spheres, a country's competitiveness depends not only on the availability of natural resources but also on the development of human capital. One of the key factors influencing economic stability and innovative progress is the education system. A competitive education system serves as the foundation for training qualified specialists capable of advancing science, technology, and ensuring economic growth. This article examines the main aspects of building a competitive education system and its role in a country's innovative development.

In Uzbekistan, a comprehensive system of continuous education has been established during the years of democratic reforms, covering all stages of the educational process. A two-tier system of higher education is in place: bachelor's and master's degrees, with the introduction of institutes for trainee researchers, research candidates, and senior research staff. During the new phase of development, the number of higher educational institutions in the country has doubled. As of November 1, 2017, there were 72 universities in Uzbekistan, including 4 academies, 27 universities, and 19 branches, 4 higher religious educational institutions and their branches. The country successfully operates branches of several leading universities from Europe and Asia. In 2018, the Tashkent University of Information Technologies and the Belarusian State University of Informatics and Radio electronics signed an agreement to establish a joint faculty of information technologies. The Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic for 2017-2021 outlines specific measures for the development of education and science. In modern conditions, there is a particular need to stimulate scientific research and innovation activities, as well as to create mechanisms for implementing its achievements in practice. To achieve these goals, a two-tier postgraduate education system has been introduced, consisting of basic doctoral studies (with a dissertation defense and the award of a PhD degree in the corresponding field of science) and doctoral studies (with a dissertation defense and the award of a Doctor of Science degree, DSc) [4].

Education is a crucial element for ensuring sustainable and long-term economic growth. A high level of education contributes to the development of a country's innovative potential, the creation of new technologies, and the implementation of effective business models. Innovations, in turn, become the basis for increasing labor productivity, creating new jobs, and improving the quality of life of the population.

The country has started the development and phased implementation of new curricula, programs for new specialties, as well as internships at joint ventures for the teaching staff of the relevant university departments. A systematic approach to conducting qualification practices for students and practical training in production is being introduced. In every university, phased training in specialty disciplines in English is being implemented in at least two groups. For promising scientific and pedagogical personnel, internships in developed countries will be introduced, and the system for training specialists at the master's level will be critically analyzed. An important aspect is the enhancement of the status of university departments, with increased responsibility for ensuring the quality of education [6].

It is planned to approve a development concept until 2030 for each university affiliated with a specific industry, and to ensure, by 2021, the recognition of at least one university from each industry by leading international ranking agencies [7]. Specific measures are being taken to improve the quality of education in universities.

A novelty in specialist training is the introduction, starting from the 2018-2019 academic year, of bachelor's degree programs with a duration of at least 3 years and master's programs with a duration of at least 1 year for certain areas of higher education. The training of master's students will be based on specialized programs in production and scientific-pedagogical fields. Core universities, based on the needs of employers, will independently develop curricula, subject programs, and approve them in coordination with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education.

Key Components of a Competitive Education System

1. High Quality of Education. For an education system to be competitive, it must provide a high level of knowledge and skills that meet international standards. It is important to improve curricula, as well as provide teachers with modern teaching methods and tools. The use of innovative technologies in teaching, such as online courses, virtual reality, and artificial intelligence, helps prepare students for work in a rapidly changing world.

2. Flexibility and Adaptability. The modern education system must be flexible, enabling it to respond quickly to changes in labor market demands. It is essential to consider that the world does not stand still, and professions that were in demand a few years ago may no longer be relevant. Therefore, educational programs should not only include traditional subjects but also elements that foster critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and initiative.

3. Internationalization of Education. In the context of globalization, it is important that educational institutions provide access to international educational resources. This allows students to gain not only national knowledge but also international experience, as well as develop skills for working in multinational and multicultural teams. Exchange programs, internships, and participation in international research projects help prepare students for global challenges.

4. Practical Orientation. An essential feature of a competitive education system is the close connection between theoretical knowledge and practical skills. This allows graduates to be ready for real professional activities immediately after completing their education. Modern educational institutions actively develop partnerships with companies and industry associations, providing students with opportunities to participate in real projects and internships.

5. Innovative Teaching Approaches. An important aspect of the competitiveness of the education system is the use of modern pedagogical technologies aimed at developing students' creative potential and independence. In this regard, particular attention should be paid to project-based learning methods, research activities, and the integration of various disciplines to solve complex problems.

The Interconnection Between Education and Innovation

Innovations are the foundation for creating a competitive economy, while quality education is the source of innovative potential. The success of innovation processes directly depends on how effectively the education system prepares specialists who are capable of creative thinking, solving non-standard tasks, and developing new technologies.

One of the brightest examples of this interaction is the support of startups and scientific research projects in universities. Many leading universities in the world have long been centers of innovation, where students, researchers, and entrepreneurs unite their efforts to create new products and technologies. In countries such as the United States, Germany, South Korea, and Finland, universities play a key role in the development of scientific and technological startups that become the foundation for economic growth.

Problems and Challenges

Despite the obvious advantages of an innovative education system, many countries face a number of problems that hinder development. One of the main problems is insufficient funding for educational institutions, leading to outdated curricula, low teacher salaries, and a lack of modern teaching materials. The issue of unequal access to quality education, especially in remote and rural areas, also remains relevant.

Additionally, a major challenge is the need for the rapid adaptation of educational programs to the rapidly changing technologies and labor market requirements. This requires educational institutions to respond quickly to new trends and develop new areas such as information technology and artificial intelligence.

Conclusion

A competitive education system is not only the foundation for training qualified specialists but also the basis for a country's successful innovative development. For a country to remain competitive on the global stage, it must invest in improving the quality of education and create conditions for the active introduction of innovative technologies. The development of a flexible, adaptive, and practical-oriented education system will be an important step toward building a knowledge-based and innovation-driven economy, which, in turn, will ensure sustainable development and improve the quality of life for the population.

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Turk tilini ikkinchi xorijiy til sifatida o'qitish

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Abstract

In today's world, the importance of multilingualism and intercultural communication is steadily increasing. The strengthening of international cooperation has heightened the need for learning various languages. For students studying in the field of English philology, learning Turkish not only enriches their linguistic knowledge but also introduces them to new cultures. This article discusses the methods, strategies, and challenges involved in teaching Turkish within English philology programs.

Keywords: teaching Turkish, English philology, communicative approach, comparative methods, linguistic competence, intercultural education.

Аннотация

На сегодняшний день важность многоязычия и межкультурной коммуникации продолжает расти. Усиление международного сотрудничества способствует увеличению потребности в изучении различных языков. Для студентов, обучающихся по направлению "Филология английского языка", изучение турецкого языка не только обогащает лингвистические знания, но и знакомит с новой культурой. В данной статье рассматриваются

методы и стратегии преподавания турецкого языка в английской филологии, а также трудности, с которыми сталкиваются преподаватели и студенты.

Ключевые слова:, преподавание турецкого языка, английская филология, коммуникативный подход, методы сравнительного анализа, лингвистическая компетенция, межкультурное обучение.

Annotatsiya

Bugungi kunda ko'ptillilik va madaniyatlara muloqotning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Xalqaro hamkorlikning kuchayishi turli tillarni o'rganishga bo'lgan ehtiyojni oshiradi. Ingliz filologiyasi yo'nalishida ta'lim olayotgan talabalar uchun turk tilini o'rganish faqat lingvistik bilimlarni boyitib qolmay, balki yangi madaniyatlar bilan tanishtiradi. Ushbu maqolada ingliz filologiyasida turk tilini o'qitishning metodlari, strategiyalari va duch kelinadigan qiyinchiliklar muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turk tilini o'qitish, ingliz filologiyasi, kommunikativ yondashuv, taqqoslash metodlari, lingvistik kompetensiya, madaniyatlara o'qitish.

Turk tilini ikkinchi xorijiy til sifatida o'qitish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu tilni o'rganish talabalarining lingvistik ko'nikmalarini boyitish, shuningdek, mintaqaviy madaniyat va iqtisodiy imkoniyatlar bilan tanishishlariga xizmat qiladi [1]. Bundan tashqari, turk tilining o'zbek tiliga yaqinligi talabalar orasida katta qiziqish uyg'otadi va o'zlashtirish jarayonini sezilarli darajada yengillashtiradi [2]. Tilni o'qitish jarayonida kommunikativ yondashuv, taqqoslash metodikasi hamda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish talabalar tilga nisbatan motivatsiyasini oshirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi [3].

Turk tili agglutinativ til bo'lib, so'zlarning ma'no va grammatik vazifalari qo'shimchalar yordamida shakllanadi. Ingliz tilida tahsil olayotgan talabalar uchun turk tilidagi so'z yasash va qo'shimchalar tizimini tushunish o'rganish jarayonini qiyinlashtirishi mumkin. Shuning uchun o'qituvchilar quyidagi jihatlarga alohida e'tibor berishlari kerak:

- Fonetik farqlar: turk tilidagi unli tovushlarning boyligi (masalan, "ü", "ö") va ingliz tilida mavjud bo'lmagan tovushlar talabalarga avvaliga qiyinchilik tug'dirishi mumkin [1].

- Grammatik tuzilma: Turk tilidagi gap tuzilmasi (SOV – ega, to'ldiruvchi, kesim tartibi) ingliz tilidagi (SVO – ega, kesim, to'ldiruvchi) tartibdan farq qiladi [2].

- Lingvistik asoslarni tushuntirishda taqqoslash metodidan foydalanish orqali talabalar bu farqlarni osonroq o'zlashtiradilar. Taqqoslash metodlari (Contrastive Methods). Ingliz va turk tillarini taqqoslash talabalarni qiyinchiliklardan ogoh qilish va ularning oldini olishga yordam beradi. Masalan, fe'l zamonlarini o'rganishda ingliz tilidagi murakkab zamon shakllari bilan turk tilining sodda fe'l shakllarini solishtirish talabalarning tushunishini yengillashtiradi [3]. Fe'l zamonlari: turk tilida faqat bir nechta oddiy zamon shakli mavjud (o'tmish, hozirgi va kelajak), ingliz tilida esa zamonlar murakkabroq.

- Ko'plik qo'shimchalari: turk tilida "-lar, -ler" ko'plik qo'shimchalari ishlatilsa, ingliz tilida ko'plik ko'rsatish ko'proq sintaktik o'zgarishlarga bog'liq. Masalan, ingliz tilida otning ko'plik shakli odatda so'ngiga "-s" yoki "-es" qo'shimchalari qo'shish orqali yasaladi, lekin ba'zi so'zlarda butunlay o'zgarish bo'ladi (child → children, man → men). Turk tilida esa otning asosiy shakli saqlanadi va faqat ko'plik qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi, bu esa soddaroq tizimni anglatadi. Ingliz tilida ko'plik fe'l bilan kelishishi (e.g., The dogs are barking) ham muhim ahamiyatga ega, turk tilida esa bunday o'zgarish ko'pincha mavjud emas.

Bu yondashuv tilshunoslikka qiziqishlari bo'lgan talabalar uchun ham til strukturasi chuqurroq o'rganishga xizmat qiladi.

Kommunikativ yondashuv (Communicative Approach)

Kommunikativ metod tilni faqat nazariy jihatdan emas, balki amalda qo'llashni o'rgatadi. Ushbu metod orqali talabalar tilni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda qanday ishlatishni o'rganadilar. Darslarda suhbat mashqlari, rolli o'yinlar, interaktiv mashqlar, munozaralar va jamoaviy ishlar kabi usullar qo'llaniladi. Talabalar tinglash, gapirish, o'qish va yozish kabi asosiy til ko'nikmalarini o'zaro bog'liq ravishda rivojlantiradilar. Masalan, kundalik hayotda qo'llaniladigan mavzular bo'yicha dialoglar o'tkazish, oziq-ovqat sotib olish, mehmonxona bron qilish, yo'l so'rash kabi vaziyatlarni mashq qilish orqali o'rganish jarayoni qiziqarli va samarali bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, autentik materiallardan (video, audio, maqola) foydalanish talabalar uchun haqiqiy til muhitini yaratadi. Ushbu metod talabalarni faol qatnashishga undab, ularning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshiradi va mustaqil fikrlash hamda erkin muloqot qilish ko'nikmasini rivojlantiradi. Turk tilini o'rganishda kommunikativ metodning afzalliklari:

- Tilni real hayotda qanday ishlatishni tushunish.
- Madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish.
- Xatolardan qo'rqmasdan so'zlash ko'nikmasini oshirish.

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirish.

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya til o'rganishning ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Turk tilini o'qitishda o'qituvchilar turk madaniyati, odatlari va ijtimoiy qadriyatlari bilan tanishtirish orqali talabalar motivatsiyasini oshiradilar. Talabalarga turk xalqining san'ati, adabiyoti va musiqa namunalarini ko'rsatish til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Shu yo'l bilan talabalar boshqa xalqlar madaniyatiga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lish ko'nikmasini ham rivojlantiradilar.

Texnologiyalar va innovatsion o'qitish vositalari

Texnologiyadan foydalanish til o'rganish jarayonini yanada samarali va qiziqarli qiladi. Talabalar uchun onlayn kurslar, mobil ilovalar, audiokitoblar va videodarslardan foydalanish o'rganishni osonlashtiradi va shaxsiylashtiradi. Ushbu texnologiyalar talabalar uchun interaktiv va individual o'quv muhitini yaratadi. Shuningdek:

- Lingvistik platformalar: Duolingo, Memrise, Rosetta Stone kabi dasturlar talabalarga mustaqil mashq qilish, grammatika, so'z boyligini oshirish va talaffuzni yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Ushbu platformalar o'yinlashgan metodika orqali o'rganish jarayonini yanada qiziqarli qiladi.

- Video va audio materiallar: turk madaniyati va tilini aks ettiruvchi videofilmlar, podkastlar, YouTube'dagi til o'rgatish kanallari orqali talabalar real til muhitiga kirishadilar va so'zlashuv nutqini yaxshiroq tushunadilar.

- Virtual muloqot platformalari: Zoom, Skype, Google Meet orqali o'qituvchi va boshqa talabalar bilan jonli muloqot qilish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Bu esa tinglash va gapirish ko'nikmalarini real vaqtda rivojlantiradi.

- Mobil ilovalar: Quizlet, Anki kabi ilovalar talabalarga yangi so'zlarni samarali yodlash va ularni muntazam takrorlash imkonini beradi.

- O'yinlar va simulyatsiyalar: interaktiv o'yinlar, til o'rgatish uchun mo'ljallangan virtual haqiqat (VR) va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR) texnologiyalari talabalarni tilni o'rganishda faol ishtirok etishga undaydi.

- Autentik materiallarga kirish: onlayn gazeta va jurnallar, bloglar, audiokitoblar va subtitrlil filmlar orqali talabalar haqiqiy va zamonaviy til bilan tanishadilar.

Ushbu vositalar orqali talabalar o'zlarining til o'rganish jarayonini mustaqil boshqarishlari va o'quv jarayonini yanada qiziqarli, interaktiv va samarali qilishlari mumkin. Bu kabi vositalar o'quv jarayoniga ijodiy yondashuv qo'shadi va talabalarni o'zlashtirishga rag'batlantiradi.

O'qitish jarayonidagi qiyinchiliklar va ularni yechish

Turk tilini o'qitishda duch kelinadigan qiyinchiliklar ham mavjud. Talabalarning ilgari turkiy tillar bilan tanish emasligi yoki tovush tizimlaridagi farqlar,

masalan, turk tilidagi yumshoq ğ yoki i tovushi kabi o'ziga xos fonetik elementlarni o'zlashtirishda qiyinchilik tug'dirishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, grammatik tuzilmalarning farqliligi, masalan, qo'shimchalarga asoslangan so'z tuzilishi yoki fe'l o'zgarishlari ba'zi talabalar uchun murakkab tuyulishi mumkin. Ayrim talabalar uchun motivatsiya darajasining pastligi yoki o'qitishga yetarlicha vaqt ajratolmaslik ham til o'rganishni qiyinlashtiradi.

Bu muammolarni hal qilish uchun quyidagi strategiyalarni qo'llash mumkin:

- **Individual yondashuv:** talabalarning ehtiyojlari, bilim darajasi va o'rganish uslublariga moslashtirilgan shaxsiy yondashuvni joriy etish. Masalan, fonetik farqlarni yaxshiroq tushunish uchun individual talaffuz mashqlari tashkil qilish.

- **Qiziqarli va amaliy mashg'ulotlar:** darslarni rolli o'yinlar, interaktiv mashqlar, suhbatlar va hayotiy vaziyatlarga asoslangan mashg'ulotlar bilan boyitish. Bu talabalar uchun dars jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va mazmunli qiladi.

- **Qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhit:** talabalar orasida hamkorlik va rag'batlantirish muhitini yaratish. Jamoaviy faoliyatlar va o'zaro yordamga asoslangan uslublar motivatsiyani oshiradi.

- **Progressni kuzatish:** har bir talabaning rivojlanishini muntazam kuzatib borish, ularga ijobiy fikr bildirish va erishilgan yutuqlarni tan olish orqali o'rganish jarayonini rag'batlantirish.

- **Autentik materiallar va texnologiyalardan foydalanish:** talabalar tilni haqiqiy kontekstda tushunishi uchun videodarslar, podkastlar va interaktiv dasturlardan foydalanish. Bu usul, ayniqsa, talaffuz va tinglash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun samarali.

- **Qo'shimcha materiallar va resurslar taqdim etish:** o'quvchilarga lug'atlar, o'quv qo'llanmalar, va qo'shimcha materiallar taqdim etish orqali tilni mustaqil o'rganish imkoniyatini kengaytirish.

Ushbu usullar o'quv jarayonini samarali, moslashuvchan va talabalarning ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilgan holda olib borishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa

Turk tilini o'qitish jarayoni zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ko'p tillilik va madaniyatlararo muloqotning rivojlanishi bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. Ingliz filologiyasi yo'nalishida o'qiyotgan talabalar uchun turk tilini o'rganish nafaqat til bilimlarini kengaytiradi, balki madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga, global miqyosda raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlashga hissa qo'shadi. Maqolada turk tilini o'rgatishda uchraydigan qiyinchiliklar va ularni yengish usullari, shuningdek, kommunikativ yondashuv, taqqoslash metodlari va texnologik vositalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi ko'rib chiqilgan. Turkiy tillar bilan tanish bo'lmagan talabalar uchun fonetik va grammatik farqlarni tushunish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin, ammo individual yondashuv, qiziqarli mashg'ulotlar, autentik materiallar va

texnologiyalar yordamida bu to'siqlarni yengish mumkin. Madaniyatlararo kompetensiya va kommunikativ yondashuv metodlari talabalarga tilni amaliyotda, real hayotdagi vaziyatlarda qo'llashni o'rgatadi. Shu bilan birga, fonetik va grammatik qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etish uchun maxsus o'quv materiallari va audio-mashqlardan foydalanish zarur. O'qituvchi tomonidan samarali strategiyalar qo'llanilganda talabalarning tilga bo'lgan ishonchi oshadi va ular global miqyosda raqobatbardosh kadr sifatida shakllanadi. Umuman olganda, turk tilini o'qitish nafaqat lingvistik bilimlarni boyitadi, balki talabalarni madaniyatlararo muloqotga tayyorlaydi, ularning shaxsiy va professional rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shadi. Shu sababli til o'qitishda ilg'or metodlarni joriy etish va o'quv jarayonini talabalar ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish nihoyatda muhimdir. Kelajakda bu metodlarni yanada kengaytirish va turli texnologiyalar yordamida o'quv jarayonini yanada interaktiv qilish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

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TIL O'QITISH NAZARIYASI VA METODIKASI

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Annotation

This article highlights the theory and methodology of language teaching as an integral part of applied linguistics. It discusses the use of modern educational technologies, communicative approaches, integrated lessons, and interactive methods to improve the effectiveness of teaching. The

article also emphasizes the importance of methodology and modern approaches in transforming linguistic knowledge into practical skills during the language learning process.

Keywords: applied linguistics, language teaching methodology, communicative approach, interactive methods, linguistic competence.

Аннотация

В данной статье теория и методика преподавания языка рассматриваются как неотъемлемая часть прикладного языкознания. Обсуждаются вопросы повышения эффективности обучения через использование современных образовательных технологий, коммуникативного подхода, интегрированных уроков и интерактивных методов. Также подчеркивается значение методики и современных подходов в преобразовании лингвистических знаний в практические навыки в процессе изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: прикладное языкознание, методика преподавания языка, коммуникативный подход, интерактивные методы, лингвистическая компетенция.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada til o‘qitish nazariyasi va metodikasi amaliy tilshunoslik fanining ajralmas qismi sifatida yoritiladi. Amaliy tilshunoslikda zamonaviy ta‘lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, kommunikativ yondashuv, integratsiyalashgan darslar va interaktiv metodlar orqali o‘qitish samaradorligini oshirish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Til o‘rganish jarayonida lingvistik bilimlarni amaliy ko‘nikmaga aylantirishda metodikaning o‘rni va zamonaviy yondashuvlarning ahamiyati ko‘rsatib o‘tiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: amaliy tilshunoslik, til o‘qitish metodikasi, kommunikativ yondashuv, interaktiv usullar, lingvistik kompetensiya.

Kirish

Amaliy tilshunoslik fanining asosiy maqsadi — tilni amaliy jihatdan o‘rganish, uni og‘zaki va yozma shakllarda samarali qo‘llashga erishishdir. Ushbu fan doirasida til o‘qitish metodikasi katta ahamiyatga ega bo‘lib, bu til o‘rgatishda qanday yondashuvlar va usullarni qo‘llash zarurligini belgilaydi. Til o‘rganishning asosiy maqsadi — tinglab tushunish, o‘qish, yozish va gapirish kabi to‘rt asosiy ko‘nikmani shakllantirish bo‘lib, bu yo‘nalishda nazariya bilan amaliyot uyg‘unligi muhimdir. Til o‘qitish metodikasi amaliy tilshunoslikda asosiy o‘rin tutadi. Metodika nazariyasi o‘quvchilarning psixologik va lingvistik xususiyatlariga asoslanadi. Zamonaviy til o‘qitish metodlari orasida kommunikativ yondashuv, CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), task-based learning va ko‘rgazmali interaktiv metodlar samarali hisoblanadi.

Amaliy tilshunoslikda o‘rganuvchilar real hayotiy muloqotga tayyorlanadi. Bu yerda o‘qituvchining metodik yondashuvi katta ahamiyatga ega: darsda rolli o‘yinlar, munozaralar, real hayotga yaqin topshiriqlardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Bularni o‘rganishda quyida berilgan metod bosqichlari orqali yanada mustahkamlash mumkin: Kommunikativ yondashuv (Communicative Approach)

Henry Widdowson kommunikativ yondashuvning asoschilaridan biri bo‘lib, u til o‘rgatishda muloqotga asoslangan yondashuvni ilgari surgan. Ushbu yondashuvda o‘quvchilar real hayotiy vaziyatlarda tilni qo‘llashga o‘rgatiladi.

Widdowson til o'rgatishda tilning faqat grammatik tuzilmasini emas, balki uning kommunikativ funksiyalarini ham o'rgatish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi; CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning)

Do Coyle, Philip Hood va David Marsh CLIL yondashuvining yetakchi tadqiqotchilaridan hisoblanadi. Ular CLILni til va fanni birgalikda o'rgatish orqali o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalarini va fanga oid bilimlarini bir vaqtda rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladigan metod sifatida ta'riflaydilar. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchilarning til o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshiradi va ularni real hayotiy vaziyatlarga tayyorlaydi; Topshiriqqa asoslangan o'qitish (Task-Based Learning) Rod Ellis topshiriqqa asoslangan o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirib, til o'rgatishda topshiriqlar orqali o'quvchilarning faol ishtirokini ta'minlashni tavsiya etgan. Ushbu yondashuvda o'quvchilarga turli topshiriqlar berish orqali til o'rgatiladi, bu esa ularning tilni real vaziyatlarda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi; Interaktiv metodlar Jeremy Harmer interaktiv metodlarning til o'rgatishdagi ahamiyatini ta'kidlab, o'qituvchilarga darslarda rol o'yinlar, munozaralar va real hayotga yaqin topshiriqlardan foydalanishni tavsiya etadi. Uning fikricha, bunday metodlar o'quvchilarning til o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi va ularni faol ishtirok etishga undaydi.

Xulosa:

Til o'qitish nazariyasi va metodikasi amaliy tilshunoslik fanining ajralmas qismidir. Til o'qitish nazariyasi va metodikasi til o'rgatish jarayonining asosiy ilmiy va amaliy tayanchi hisoblanadi. Har bir yondashuvning o'ziga xos afzalliklari bo'lib, ularni o'quvchilar ehtiyoji va kontekstiga qarab tanlash muhimdir. Til o'rgatishda zamonaviy metodik yondashuvlar va texnologiyalarni uyg'unlashtirish ta'lim sifatini oshirishda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Metodik yondashuvlar tilni chuqur va samarali o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. O'quvchilarda til kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda interaktiv, kommunikativ va amaliy usullarning o'rnini beqiyosdir. Kelajakda ham zamonaviy metodikalar asosida til o'rgatish samaradorligini oshirish ilmiy va amaliy jihatdan dolzarb masala bo'lib qoladi.

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The Role of Motivation in Foreign Language Learning

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Abstract

Motivation is one of the most significant affective factors influencing success in foreign language learning. This paper investigates the role of motivation by analyzing theoretical and empirical studies in the field of second language acquisition. Drawing on the works of Gardner, Dörnyei, and Deci & Ryan, the study examines intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, integrative and instrumental orientations, and the L2 Motivational Self System. Findings suggest that motivation is not only a prerequisite but a sustaining factor that influences learners' attitudes, strategies, and achievement in foreign language contexts. Recommendations are offered for teachers to foster long-term motivation in classrooms.

Keywords: Motivation, Foreign Language Learning, Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Language Acquisition, Integrative Motivation, Educational Psychology.

Anotatsiya

Motivatsiya bu chet tili o'rganishda muvaffaqiyatga erishishga ta'sir qiluvchi eng muhim omillardan biridir. Ushbu maqola ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish sohasidagi nazariy va empirik tadqiqotlarni tahlil qilish orqali motivatsiyaning rolini o'rganadi. Gardner, Dörnyei hamda Deci va Ryanning tadqiqotlariga asoslangan holda, maqolada ichki va tashqi motivatsiya, integrativ va instrumental yo'nalishlar hamda L2 o'z o'ziga motivatsiya berish tizimi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, motivatsiya nafaqat zaruriy shart, balki chet tilini o'rganish davomida o'quvchilarning munosabati, strategiyasi va yutuqlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omilidir. O'qituvchilarga dars jarayonida uzoq muddatli motivatsiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'z: Motivatsiya, Chet tilini o'rganish, Ichki motivatsiya, Tashqi motivatsiya, Tilni o'zlashtirish, Integrativ motivatsiya, Ta'lim psixologiyasi.

Аннотация

Мотивация является одним из наиболее значимых аффективных факторов, влияющих на успех в изучении иностранного языка. В данной статье рассматривается роль мотивации на основе анализа теоретических и эмпирических исследований в области изучения второго языка. Основываясь на трудах Гарднера, Дёрньеи, а также Деси и Райана, исследование

рассматривает внутреннюю и внешнюю мотивацию, интегративную и инструментальную направленности, а также систему мотивационного «Я» (L2 Motivational Self System). Результаты показывают, что мотивация является не только необходимым условием, но и устойчивым фактором, влияющим на отношение учащихся, их стратегии и достижения в контексте изучения иностранного языка. В статье предлагаются рекомендации для учителей по поддержанию долгосрочной мотивации на уроках.

Ключевые слова: Мотивация, Изучение иностранного языка, Внутренняя мотивация, Внешняя мотивация, Усвоение языка, Интегративная мотивация, Педагогическая психология.

1. Introduction

Learning a foreign language is a complex process involving cognitive, social, and emotional factors. Among these, motivation is consistently regarded as one of the key predictors of success (Dörnyei, 2001). Without sufficient motivation, learners may not engage with the language actively, nor persevere through challenges. Early studies by Gardner and Lambert (1972) emphasized the social and emotional aspects of motivation, distinguishing between integrative (desire to integrate with the culture of the target language) and instrumental (learning for practical benefits) motivation. This paper explores how different types and theories of motivation influence language learning, and how educators can support learners to maintain high levels of motivation.

2. Methods

This paper is based on a qualitative review of major theoretical frameworks and empirical studies related to motivation in second language acquisition (SLA). Sources include peer-reviewed journal articles, academic books, and case studies published between 1990 and 2020. The works of Zoltán Dörnyei, Richard Gardner, Edward Deci, and Richard Ryan were closely analyzed. The selection criteria focused on studies discussing the types of motivation, their impact on learning outcomes, and pedagogical implications. No original data were collected; rather, the study synthesizes key findings to draw comprehensive conclusions.

3. Results

The literature suggests that integrative motivation often results in greater long-term success in language learning. Learners motivated by a desire to connect with the target culture tend to show more persistence and deeper engagement (Gardner & Lambert, 1972). On the other hand, instrumental motivation, such as learning a language for job opportunities, can be effective in the short term but may not lead to sustained learning.

Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (1985) differentiates between intrinsic (internal) and extrinsic (external) motivation. Intrinsically motivated learners enjoy the process itself and are more self-directed, while extrinsically motivated learners depend more on rewards or pressures.

Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System adds a new dimension, showing that learners with a strong ideal self-image as a successful language speaker are more likely to remain committed (Dörnyei, 2005). His model includes:

- Ideal L2 self (who the learner wants to become),
- Ought-to L2 self (who the learner thinks they should become), and
- L2 learning experience (situational factors in the classroom).

4. Discussion

Understanding motivation allows educators to design effective learning environments. Teachers can nurture intrinsic motivation by using meaningful tasks, offering autonomy, and encouraging goal-setting. Incorporating cultural elements and authentic materials can enhance integrative motivation. Additionally, creating a supportive classroom atmosphere and recognizing individual progress fosters positive L2 learning experiences.

Educators should also be aware of demotivating factors such as high anxiety, negative peer influence, and irrelevant curriculum. Motivation should be viewed as dynamic—it can fluctuate depending on context, feedback, and personal goals. Ultimately, motivation is not just a psychological state but a powerful determinant of learner success in foreign language education.

5. Conclusion

Motivation is a multifaceted concept that significantly influences foreign language learning. Both intrinsic and extrinsic factors play crucial roles, and teachers must recognize and foster different types of motivation to support student success. Theoretical models such as Gardner's and Dörnyei's provide valuable insights into learner behavior, and their implications can help improve language teaching methodologies. Creating engaging, relevant, and supportive classroom environments is essential to developing and sustaining student motivation.

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МУЗЫКИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ НЕМЕЦКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich maktabda nemis tilini o'qitishning samarali vositasi sifatida musiqiy hamrohlikdan foydalanish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida musiqaning fonematik idrok etish, so'z boyligi, grammatik va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga ta'sirining pedagogik-psixologik jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Muvaffaqiyatli ta'lim loyihalariga misollar keltirilib, musiqani til o'qitishga integratsiya qilish samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi. Qayd etilishicha, musiqiy elementlar til o'rganish jarayonini boshlang'ich maktab yoshidagi bolalar uchun yanada qiziqarli, rag'batlantiruvchi va qulayroq qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: nemis tili, boshlang'ich maktab, musiqiy hamrohlik, til ko'nikmalari, fonemik ong, lug'at, grammatika, muloqot qobiliyatlari, musiqiy tayyorgarlik, treningdagi qo'shiqlar

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности использования музыкального сопровождения как эффективного средства обучения немецкому языку в начальной школе. Анализируются педагогические и психологические аспекты влияния музыки на развитие фонематического восприятия, словарного запаса, грамматических и коммуникативных навыков у младших школьников. Приводятся примеры успешных образовательных проектов, подтверждающих эффективность интеграции музыки в языковое обучение. Отмечается, что музыкальные элементы делают процесс изучения языка более увлекательным, мотивирующим и доступным для детей младшего школьного возраста.

Ключевые слова: немецкий язык, начальная школа, музыкальное сопровождение, языковые навыки, фонематическое восприятие, словарный запас, грамматика, коммуникативные навыки, музыкальное обучение, песни в обучении

Annotation: This article considers the possibilities of using musical accompaniment as an effective means of teaching German in elementary school. It analyzes pedagogical and psychological aspects of music's influence on the development of phonemic perception, vocabulary, grammatical and communicative skills in primary school students. Examples of successful educational projects confirming the effectiveness of integrating music into language learning are given. It is noted that musical elements make the process of language learning more exciting, motivating and accessible for primary school children.

Keywords: German language, elementary school, musical accompaniment, language skills, phonemic awareness, vocabulary, grammar, communicative skills, musical learning, songs in learning.

Современные исследования в области педагогики и психологии подтверждают, что музыка является эффективным инструментом для развития языковых навыков у младших школьников. Интеграция музыкальных элементов в образовательный процесс способствует улучшению фонематического восприятия, расширению словарного запаса, а также развитию грамматических и коммуникативных навыков.

1. Роль музыки в развитии фонематического восприятия.

Исследования показывают, что музыкальная деятельность способствует улучшению фонематической осведомленности у детей. Например, в исследовании, проведенном в Университете Гиссена, дети, участвующие в музыкальных программах, продемонстрировали улучшение в таких областях, как рифмовка и сегментация слогов, что является важными компонентами фонематического восприятия. ([IDW Online](#))

2. Музыка как средство расширения словарного запаса. Песни и

ритмичные стихотворения помогают детям запоминать новые слова и фразы. Например, проект "SprachSpielGesang" в Австрии использовал песни для обучения детей структурам языка, что способствовало улучшению их языковых навыков. ([forschungslandkarte.at](#))

3. Музыка и развитие грамматических навыков. Музыкальные

занятия помогают детям осваивать грамматические структуры через повторение и ритмическую организацию языка. Это способствует лучшему усвоению грамматических правил и их применению в речи.

4. Музыка и коммуникативные навыки. Музыкальная деятельность

способствует развитию коммуникативных навыков, таких как уверенность в себе, понимание задач и расширение словарного запаса. Проект "Durch Musik zur Sprache" в Германии показал, что дети, участвующие в музыкальных программах, улучшили свои коммуникативные навыки. ([DIE WELT+2uni-bremen.de+2Universität Münster+2](#))

5. Практическое применение музыкального сопровождения в

обучении немецкому языку. Внедрение музыкальных элементов в уроки немецкого языка может включать:

- Использование песен для обучения новым словам и фразам.
- Применение ритмичных стихотворений для улучшения фонематического восприятия.
- Включение музыкальных игр для развития грамматических навыков.
- Организацию музыкальных выступлений для улучшения коммуникативных навыков.

Заключение: Интеграция музыки в процесс обучения немецкому языку в начальной школе является эффективным методом, способствующим развитию различных языковых навыков у детей. Использование музыкальных элементов помогает детям легче и быстрее осваивать язык, а также делает процесс обучения более увлекательным и мотивирующим.

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TURKIY TILLARNI O'RGATISH METODLARI VA ULARNING XALQARO TA'LIMDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola turkiy tillarni o'qitishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari va metodologik asoslarini tahlil qiladi hamda mazkur tillarning global miqyosdagi o'rni va ahamiyatini keng qamrovli tarzda ochib beradi. Maqolada turkiy tillarning boy lingvistik xususiyatlari, ularni o'rganish jarayonidagi murakkabliklar va osonlashtiruvchi omillar, shuningdek, turli mamlakatlarda qo'llanilayotgan innovatsion o'qitish strategiyalari va texnologiyalari batafsil ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, turkiy tillarning xalqaro siyosiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy va ilmiy sohalaridagi ta'siri, global integratsiya jarayonlaridagi strategik roli hamda kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari chuqur tahlil etiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari turkiy tillarni o'qitish amaliyotini yanada takomillashtirish, o'quvchilarning til o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish va turkiy tillarning xalqaro maydondagi nufuzini mustahkamlashga qaratilgan amaliy xulosalar va istiqbolli tavsiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turkiy tillar, lingvistik tahlil, global o'rin, madaniy meros, siyosiy ta'sir, iqtisodiy aloqalar, xalqaro integratsiya, til siyosati, pedagogik innovatsiyalar.

Annotation. This article analyzes modern trends and methodological foundations of teaching Turkic languages and comprehensively reveals the role and importance of these languages on a global scale. The article examines in detail the rich linguistic features of Turkic languages, the complexities and facilitating factors in their learning process, as well as innovative teaching strategies and technologies used in different countries. In addition, the impact of Turkic languages in the international political, economic, cultural and scientific spheres, their strategic role in global integration processes and future development prospects are analyzed in depth. The research results include practical conclusions and promising recommendations aimed at further improving the practice of teaching Turkic languages, increasing the effectiveness of students' language acquisition, and strengthening the prestige of Turkic languages in the international arena.

Keywords: Turkish languages, linguistic analysis, global significance, cultural heritage, political influence, economic relations, international integration, language policy, pedagogical innovations.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются современные тенденции и методологические основы преподавания тюркских языков, а также всесторонне анализируется их роль и значение в глобальном масштабе. Подробно исследуются богатые лингвистические особенности тюркских языков, сложности и способствующие факторы в процессе их изучения, а также инновационные стратегии и технологии преподавания, применяемые в различных образовательных контекстах. Кроме того, анализируется влияние тюркских языков в международных политических, экономических, культурных и научных сферах, их стратегическая роль в процессах глобальной интеграции и перспективы дальнейшего развития. Результаты исследования включают практические выводы и перспективные рекомендации, направленные на совершенствование практики преподавания тюркских языков, повышение эффективности усвоения языка учащимися и укрепление престижа тюркских языков на международной арене.

Ключевые слова: тюркские языки, лингвистический анализ, глобальное значение, культурное наследие, политическое влияние, экономические связи, международная интеграция, языковая политика, педагогические инновации.

Turkiy tillar oilasi jahon tillari xazinasining eng qadimiy va serqirra tarmoqlaridan biri bo‘lib, o‘zining boy tarixi, keng geografik areali va millionlab so‘zlashuvchilari bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu tillarda so‘zlashuvchilar soni ikki yuz milliondan oshib, ular Yevrosiyoning ulkan hududida, Balkan yarim orolidan Sharqiy Sibirgacha bo‘lgan kengliklarda tarqalgan. O‘zbek tili ham o‘zining o‘ziga xosligi, boy adabiyoti va madaniy merosi bilan bu ulkan til oilasining eng yorqin vakillaridan biri hisoblanadi.

XXI asrning dinamik globallashuv jarayoni turli xalqlar va madaniyatlar o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqalarni misli ko‘rilmagan darajada kuchaytirdi. Bunday sharoitda turkiy tillarni o‘rganish va o‘rgatish masalasi strategik ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Turkiy tillarni mukammal bilish nafaqat boy tarixiy va madaniy merosni chuqur anglash, balki zamonaviy siyosat, dinamik iqtisodiyot va serqirra xalqaro munosabatlar sohalarida muvaffaqiyatli faoliyat yuritish uchun muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Shu bois, turkiy tillarni o‘qitish uslubiyatini zamon talablariga mos ravishda takomillashtirish, o‘quv jarayoniga eng so‘nggi pedagogik texnologiyalarni faol joriy etish, mavjud o‘quv materiallarini har tomonlama optimallashtirish va o‘qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyasini oshirish bugungi kunning eng dolzarb vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, turkiy tillarning bugungi kundagi global o‘rnini aniq belgilash, ularning xalqaro miqyosdagi ko‘p qirrali ahamiyatini har tomonlama ochib berish ham g‘oyat muhimdir. Ushbu ilmiy maqola ana shu hayotiy ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan masalalarni chuqur tahlil qilishga bag‘ishlanadi. Turkiy tillarni o‘qitish uslubiyatiga bag‘ishlangan ilmiy adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko‘rsatadiki, bu sohada turli xil innovatsion yondashuvlar va samarali metodlar ishlab chiqilgan va amaliyotga joriy etilmoqda. An‘anaviy grammatika-tarjima usulidan tortib, kommunikativ usulning zamonaviy talqinlari, interaktiv ta’limning dinamik metodlari, talabalarning mustaqil ijodiy faoliyatini rag‘batlantiruvchi loyiha asosidagi ta’lim, vaqt

va makon chegaralarini buzib o'tuvchi masofaviy o'qitish kabi ilg'or texnologiyalarga asoslangan uslublar keng qo'llanilmoqda.

Xususan, kommunikativ usul o'quvchilarning real hayotiy vaziyatlarda tilni erkin va samarali qo'llay olish ko'nikmalarini har tomonlama rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan bo'lib, bunda asosiy e'tibor grammatik qoidalarni yodlashdan ko'ra, amaliy muloqotga qaratiladi. Interaktiv metodlar o'quv jarayonida talabalarning faol ishtirokini ta'minlab, ularning mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy qobiliyatlarini o'stiradi va o'zaro hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi. Loyiha asosidagi ta'lim esa o'quvchilarga mustaqil ravishda dolzarb mavzular bo'yicha chuqur tadqiqot olib borish, mavjud muammolarni kreativ hal etish va olingan natijalarni ishonarli tarzda taqdim etish noyob imkoniyatini beradi. Masofaviy o'qitish esa geografik to'siqlarni bartaraf etib, dunyoning turli burchaklaridagi o'quvchilarga turkiy tillarni qulay va samarali o'rganish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Turkiy tillarning dunyodagi o'rniga bag'ishlangan adabiyotlar esa bu tillarning nafaqat boy tarixi va bebaho madaniy merosini, balki ularning global siyosiy va iqtisodiy aloqalardagi strategik ahamiyatini ham chuqur yoritadi. Turkiy tillar turli xalqlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro muloqotning muhim vositasi bo'lish bilan birga, ularning o'ziga xos madaniy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarini saqlab qolish va kelajak avlodlarga bezavol yetkazishda ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. Markaziy Osiyo mintaqasi, Turkiya Respublikasi, Ozarbayjon Respublikasi kabi davlatlarning siyosiy barqarorligi va iqtisodiy yuksalishida turkiy tillarning o'rni beqiyosdir. Bundan tashqari, turkiy tillarni mukammal bilish orqali jahon adabiyoti durdonalari, san'atining noyob namunalari va ilmiy fikrining eng so'nggi yutuqlarini bevosita o'rganish imkoniyati mavjud.

Muhokama jarayonida shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, turkiy tillarni o'qitish uslubiyatini yanada takomillashtirishda o'quvchilarning individual yosh xususiyatlari, ularning qiziqishlari va ta'limiy ehtiyojlarini har tomonlama hisobga olish g'oyat zarurdir. Shuningdek, turkiy til o'qituvchilarining kasbiy mahoratini muntazam ravishda oshirish, ularni zamonaviy o'qitish metodlari va innovatsion texnologiyalari bilan doimiy ravishda tanishtirib borish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turkiy tillarning xalqaro maydondagi nufuzini mustahkamlash uchun esa oqilona til siyosatini yuritish, turkiy tillarda yuqori sifatli o'quv materiallari va boy kontentini yaratishni har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash, xalqaro miqyosda turkiy tillarni faol targ'ib qilish lozim. Turkiy tillarni o'qitish uslubiyatiga nazar tashlar ekanmiz, zamonaviy pedagogikaning ilg'or yutuqlari bilan qadimiy lingvistik an'analarning o'zaro uyg'unlashuvi ko'zga tashlanadi. Bugungi kunda o'qituvchi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki o'quvchining intellektual va shaxsiy kamolotiga yo'l ko'rsatuvchi murabbiy sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Interaktiv metodlar, munozarali darslar, ijodiy loyihalar o'quvchini faol izlanishga undaydi, uning tanqidiy fikrlash va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi.

Turkiy tillarning dunyodagi o'rnini haqida mulohaza yuritish ekanimiz, ularning nafaqat etnik aloqalarni mustahkamlovchi vosita, balki boy madaniy merosning asrab-avaylovchisi ekanligini anglaymiz. Asrlar osha shakllangan adabiyot, san'at, folklor namunalarini o'rganish orqali o'quvchi turkiy xalqlarining ruhiyatini, dunyoqarashini chuqur idrok etadi. Bu esa uning ma'naviy olamini boyitadi, o'zligini anglashiga yordam beradi. Globallashtirish sharoitida turkiy tillarni bilishning iqtisodiy va siyosiy ahamiyati ham beqiyosdir. Xalqaro savdo-sotiq, diplomatik munosabatlar, turizm sohalarida turkiy tillarni mukammal egallagan mutaxassislar talab ortib bormoqda. Bu esa yosh avlod uchun yangi imkoniyatlar eshigini ochadi, ularning kelajakda muvaffaqiyatga erishishiga zamin yaratadi. Ammo shuni ham unutmaslik kerakki, til o'rgatish jarayoni faqatgina lingvistik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish bilan cheklanmaydi. U shuningdek, o'quvchida boshqa madaniyatlarga hurmat, tolerantlik tuyg'ularini uyg'otishi, uni dunyo fuqarosi sifatida tarbiyalashi lozim. Turkiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonida turli xalqlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunish va hamjihatlik rishtalari mustahkamlanadi.

Xulosa. Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, turkiy tillarni o'qitish – bu nafaqat bilim berish, balki inson qalbiga ma'naviyat urug'ini qadash, uni milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalash demakdir. Zamonaviy uslubiyot va texnologiyalardan oqilona foydalanish, o'qituvchining fidoyiligi va o'quvchining intilishi tufayli turkiy tillar jahon sivilizatsiyasining yorqin bir qismi sifatida o'zining munosib o'rnini egallaydi. Kelajak avlodlar bu boy merosni asrab-avaylab, yanada rivojlantirishga mas'uldirlar.

Turkiy tillar o'zining boy tarixiy ildizlari, madaniy merosi va tilshunoslik xususiyatlari bilan jahon tillari orasida alohida o'rin egallaydi. Ushbu tillarni o'qitish jarayonini zamonaviy metodlar, innovatsion texnologiyalar va ilg'or tajribalarga asoslanib rivojlantirish, ularning xalqaro nufuzini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi. Shu bilan birga, o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish, o'quv materiallarini yangilash hamda davlat darajasida samarali til siyosatini yo'lga qo'yish — til ta'limining sifatini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Kelgusida olib boriladigan ilmiy va amaliy izlanishlar esa turkiy tillarning global maydondagi rolini mustahkamlashga asos bo'ladi.

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TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation - This article discusses the influence of teaching English on language acquisition, especially, education provides creative inspiration for the spirituality of the people of Uzbekistan. It helps us discover the best abilities of the up and coming generation, while continuously improving the skills of people. Education helps elucidate and pass down the wisdom and experiences of the older generation to the younger. Young people, with their budding talents and thirst for knowledge, begin to understand spirituality through education.

Keywords: Language Learning, education, technology integration, language proficiency, educational equity, pedagogical innovation.

Annotatsiya – Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishning til o'zlashtirishga ta'siri, xususan, ta'lim O'zbekiston xalqi ma'naviyati uchun ijodiy ilhom baxsh etishi haqida so'z boradi. Bu bizga o'sib kelayotgan va kelajak avlodning eng yaxshi qobiliyatlarini kashf qilishimizga yordam beradi, shu bilan birga pestle ta'lim ko'nikmalarini doimiy ravishda takomillashtirib borish keksa avlodning donoligi va tajribalarini yoshlarga etkazishga yordam beradi. Yoshlar o'zlarining iqtidori, bilimga tashnaligi bilan ma'naviyatni ta'lim-tarbiya orqali anglay boshlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til o'rganish, ta'lim, texnologiya integratsiyasi, tilni bilish, ta'lim tengligi, pedagogik innovatsiyalar.

Аннотация - В этой статье обсуждается влияние преподавания английского языка на усвоение языка, в частности, образование дает творческое вдохновение для духовности народа Узбекистана. Оно помогает нам раскрыть лучшие способности подрастающего поколения, постоянно совершенствуя навыки пестика. Образование помогает разъяснить и передать мудрость и опыт старшего поколения молодому. Молодые люди с их зарождающимися талантами и жадой знаний начинают понимать духовность через образование.

Ключевые слова: изучение языка, образование, интеграция технологий, владение языком, образовательное равенство, педагогические инновации.

INTRODUCTION. The reforms in progress open new opportunities for the young generation of our country to reveal their industriousness. The potential of the individual has most favorable genetic has with the Uzbeks the country is rich in capable, gifted young people who have managed to associate themselves with the best achievements of the world in science, technology, philosophy and law while retaining their affiliation with their people. They are the most enterprising section of the society and have the most positive impact on the whole of the nation, instilling confidence in its capability"

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The perspective in reform radically the whole sphere of education to put the content, forms and methodology of training to real requirements of the society, to make higher and secondary schools free from conservatism and formalism which have given deep roots during the former regime has

appeared. The intensive process is going on for the creation of new types of educational institutions: professional colleges, academic lyceums. The creation of demographic conditions and local requirements of various specialists will significantly influence the social and economic these or those regions of our republic development of these or those regions of our republic.

RESULTS. The system of higher education has got broad development and education have been taking into consideration in Uzbekistan. The president SH. Mirziyayev says that children young people are our future. Because, they will create future. Educational task is teaching with new technologies and new ways of the training the children. Then the children are very interested in subject and understand the same theme very fast. So the teacher must love and know his own job and children. Many teachers of second language have shown great interest in how some of the techniques in Storyline might be adapted and developed for stimulating language use with learners.

Teaching English to speakers to other languages is both challenging and rewarding. More and more internationally minded people are choosing to teach English as a second language both in the United states and abroad. Whether in the United states, another English speaking country or in country or in countries around the world, the teacher of English as a second language will need to keep in mind the following simple guidelines. Teaching a foreign language means first and foremost the formation and development of pupil's habits and skills in hearing, speaking, reading and effectively if we don't know and take into account the psychology of habits and skills, the ways of forming them, the influence of formerly acquired habits on the formation of new ones and many other necessary factors that psychology can supply us with.

DISCUSSION. Effective learning of a foreign language depends to a great extent on pupils' memory. That is why a teacher must know how he can help his pupils to successfully memorize and retain in memory the language material they learn. Pedagogics is the science concerned with the teaching and education of the younger generation. Since Methods also deals with the problems of teaching and education, it is most closely related to pedagogics. To study foreign language teaching one must know pedagogics. One branch of pedagogics is called didactics. Didactics studies general ways of teaching in schools. Methods as compared to didactics, studies the specific ways of teaching a definite subject. Thus it may be considered special didactics. In the foreign language teaching, as well as in the teaching of mathematics, history and other subjects taught in schools, general principles of didactics are applied and in their turn, influence and enrich didactics. For example, the so-called "principle of visualization" was first introduced in teaching foreign languages.

CONCLUSION. To sum up, the integration of learning can has become one of the fundamental principles of didactics and is used in teaching all school subjects without exception. Programmed instruction was first applied teaching mathematics. Now through didactics it is used in teaching many subjects, including foreign languages.

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Linguistic Meaning in Language Pedagogy: Analyzing Types of Meaning, Word-Meaning, and Morphemic Meaning for Effective Teaching

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Abstract

This article explores the intricate relationship between linguistic meaning—specifically, types of meaning, word-meaning, and morphemic meaning—and its pedagogical implications in modern language teaching. By aligning with the conference theme "Language Teaching Methodology and Pedagogy," the study highlights how understanding semantic structures can enhance linguistic competence and intercultural communication. The discussion bridges theoretical linguistics and practical classroom innovations, emphasizing the role of morphemic analysis and lexical semantics in fostering language acquisition.

Keywords: linguistic meaning, word-meaning, morphemes, language pedagogy, semantic competence

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada lingvistik ma'no (xususan, ma'no turlari, so'z ma'nosi va morfemik ma'no) va zamonaviy til o'qitishdagi uning pedagogik oqibatlari o'rtasidagi murakkab bog'liqlik tadqiq etiladi. Konferensiyaning "Til o'qitish metodikasi va pedagogikasi" mavzusiga mos ravishda, tadqiqot semantik tuzilmalarni tushunish lingvistik kompetensiya va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani qanday yaxshilashi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi. Munozara nazariy lingvistika va sinfdagi amaliy innovatsiyalarni birlashtirib, til o'zlashtirishga yordam berishda morfemik tahlil va leksik semantikaning roliga alohida e'tibor qaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvistik ma'no, so'z ma'nosi, morfemalar, til pedagogikasi, semantik kompetensiya

Аннотация

В данной статье исследуется сложная взаимосвязь между лингвистическим значением (а именно, типами значения, значением слова и морфемным значением) и его педагогическими последствиями в современном преподавании языков. Соответствуя теме конференции «Методология и педагогика преподавания языков», исследование подчеркивает, как понимание семантических структур может улучшить лингвистическую компетенцию и межкультурную коммуникацию. Обсуждение объединяет теоретическую лингвистику и практические инновации в классе, уделяя особое внимание роли морфемного анализа и лексической семантики в содействии усвоению языка.

Ключевые слова: лингвистическое значение, значение слова, морфемы, педагогика языка, семантическая компетенция

Introduction

The study of linguistic meaning is fundamental to understanding how language functions as a system of communication. Meaning operates at multiple levels - lexical, morphological, and contextual - each contributing to the way speakers interpret and produce language. This article examines three core aspects of meaning:

- Types of Meaning: The distinction between denotative (literal meaning), connotative (cultural/emotional associations), and collocative (word-pairing tendencies) meanings (Lyons, 1977).

- **Word-Meaning:** How individual lexemes carry semantic content, including challenges like polysemy (multiple meanings, e.g., "bank") and homonymy (same form, unrelated meanings, e.g., "bat").

- **Morphemic Meaning:** The smallest units of meaning (e.g., un-, -able), which modify word semantics and grammar (Aronoff & Fudeman, 2011).

This exploration aligns with the conference's focus on innovative language teaching methodologies, proposing that explicit instruction in semantic structures enhances linguistic competence and intercultural communication.

1. Theoretical Foundations of Meaning

1.1. Types of Meaning

- **Denotative Meaning:** The dictionary definition (e.g., "rose" as a flower).
- **Connotative Meaning:** Subjective associations (e.g., "rose" symbolizing love).
- **Collocative Meaning:** Expected word pairings (e.g., "heavy rain" vs. *"strong rain"*) (Cruse, 1986).

Pedagogical Implication: Teaching connotative differences across cultures avoids misunderstandings (e.g., "owl" signifies wisdom in Europe but bad luck in India).

1.2. Word-Meaning and Semantic Relations

- **Polysemy:** A word with related meanings (e.g., "head" of a person/company).
- **Homonymy:** Words with identical forms but unrelated meanings (e.g., "bear" [animal] vs. "bear" [tolerate]).

Classroom Activity: Use semantic webs to map polysemous words, aiding retention (Bowers & Kirby, 2010).

1.3. Morphemic Meaning and Word Formation

- **Derivational Morphemes:** Change word class (e.g., -ness in "happiness").
- **Inflectional Morphemes:** Modify grammar (e.g., -ed for past tense).

Example: Breaking down "unhappiness":

- un- (negation) + happy (root) + -ness (noun-forming suffix).

Teaching Tool: Morpheme Puzzles - students assemble morphemes to form words.

2. Practical Applications in Language Teaching

2.1. Morpheme-Based Vocabulary Instruction

- **Why It Works:** Morphemes are reusable; learning -able helps decode "readable," "washable," etc.

- **Activity:** "Morpheme Detective" - students identify affixes in authentic texts (e.g., news articles).

2.2. Addressing Polysemy with Technology

- **AI Chatbots:** Simulate conversations using polysemous words (e.g., "Can you file this paper?" vs. "Where's the file?").

- Virtual Labs: Interactive exercises where learners drag meanings to correct word uses.

2.3. Cross-Linguistic Challenges

- Problem: Morpheme transparency varies (e.g., Turkish agglutination vs. English irregularity).

- Solution: Contrastive analysis (compare -lar [Turkish plural] with -s in English).

3. Challenges and Recommendations

3.1. Common Pitfalls

- Overloading Students: Introducing too many morphemes at once.

Fix: Scaffold instruction (start with common prefixes like un-, re-).

- Cultural Nuances: Connotative mismatches (e.g., "dragon" as negative in Chinese vs. heroic in Western myths).

3.2. Future Directions

- Gamification: Apps like Quizlet for morpheme drills.

- Corpus Linguistics: Use tools like COCA to teach collocations.

Conclusion

Integrating meaning-focused instruction - especially morphemic and lexical semantics - into language curricula empowers learners to decode language systematically. This approach aligns with the conference's emphasis on modern pedagogies, leveraging technology (AI, virtual labs) and intercultural frameworks. Future research could explore morpheme acquisition in L2 learners using eye-tracking technology.

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PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ANNOTATION

This article examines phraseological units as essential and unique elements of the English language, playing a vital role in both spoken and written communication. It explores their semantic features, including idiomaticity, metaphorical meaning, and non-compositionality, as well as their structural characteristics such as fixedness and lexical integrity. Various classifications—based on origin, grammatical structure, and degree of semantic cohesion—are analyzed to provide a comprehensive understanding of phraseological diversity. The paper emphasizes the significance of phraseological units in enhancing communicative competence, enriching vocabulary, and fostering cultural awareness by reflecting the history, values, and worldview of native speakers. It also discusses the cognitive and pragmatic functions of phraseological expressions in discourse. Additionally, the article addresses the challenges phraseological units pose for language learners, particularly in terms of interpretation and usage, due to their figurative nature and cultural specificity. Drawing on modern linguistic theories—including cognitive linguistics, corpus linguistics, and phraseodidactics—the article presents practical methods and didactic strategies for the effective teaching and learning of phraseological units in both ESL and EFL contexts. Numerous authentic examples and usage contexts are provided to illustrate their function in real-life communication and to highlight their importance in achieving language fluency and cultural competence.

Keywords: Phraseological units, idioms, fixed expressions, figurative meaning, collocations, linguistic structure, semantic unity, English language teaching, cultural context.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilining muhim va o'ziga xos unsurlaridan biri bo'lgan frazeologik birliklar tahlil qilinadi. Ular og'zaki va yozma nutqda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Maqolada bu birliklarning semantik xususiyatlari — idiomatiklik, metaforik ma'no va kompozitsion bo'lmaslik, shuningdek, ularning strukturaviy xususiyatlari — barqarorlik va leksik yaxlitlik kabi jihatlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Frazeologik birliklarning kelib chiqishi, grammatik tuzilishi va semantik yaxlitlik darajasi asosida turli tasniflari tahlil qilinadi, bu esa frazeologik xilma-xillikni to'liq tushunishga xizmat qiladi.

Maqolada frazeologik birliklarning kommunikativ kompetensiyani oshirish, so'z boyligini kengaytirish va madaniy ongini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati alohida ta'kidlanadi, chunki bu birliklar ona tilida so'zlashuvchilarning tarixi, qadriyatlari va dunyoqarashini aks ettiradi. Bundan tashqari, frazeologik ifodalar nutqdagi kognitiv va pragmatik funksiyalari nuqtai nazaridan ham muhokama qilinadi.

Shuningdek, maqolada til o'rganuvchilar uchun frazeologik birliklarni to'g'ri tushunish va qo'llashda yuzaga keladigan muammolar, ayniqsa ularning obrazli tabiati va madaniy xosligi tufayli vujudga keladigan qiyinchiliklar ko'rib chiqiladi. Kognitiv lingvistik, korpus lingvistik va frazeodidaktika kabi zamonaviy lingvistik nazariyalarga tayanilgan holda, ESL (Ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida) va EFL (Ingliz tili xorijiy til sifatida) kontekstlarida frazeologik birliklarni samarali o'qitish va o'rganish uchun amaliy usullar va didaktik strategiyalar taqdim etiladi.

Ko'plab autentik misollar va qo'llanilish kontekstlari frazeologik birliklarning real kommunikatsiyadagi funksiyasini yoritib beradi hamda til ravonligi va madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani shakllantirishdagi ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazeologik birliklar, idiomalar, barqaror iboralar, ko'chma ma'no, kollokatsiyalar, lingvistik tuzilma, semantik yaxlitlik, ingliz tili o'qitish, madaniy kontekst.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются фразеологические единицы как важные и уникальные элементы английского языка, играющие ключевую роль как в устной, так и в письменной коммуникации. Анализируются их семантические особенности, включая идиоматичность, метафоричность и неконпозициональность, а также структурные характеристики, такие как устойчивость и лексическая цельность. Рассматриваются различные классификации фразеологических единиц — по происхождению, грамматической структуре и степени семантической спаянности — с целью обеспечения всестороннего понимания их разнообразия.

В статье подчеркивается значение фразеологических единиц для развития коммуникативной компетенции, обогащения словарного запаса и формирования культурной осведомленности, так как они отражают историю, ценности и мировоззрение носителей языка. Также обсуждаются когнитивные и прагматические функции фразеологических выражений в дискурсе.

Дополнительно в статье поднимаются трудности, которые фразеологические единицы представляют для изучающих язык, особенно в интерпретации и употреблении, ввиду их образности и культурной специфики. Основываясь на современных лингвистических теориях — таких как когнитивная лингвистика, корпусная лингвистика и фразеодидактика — статья предлагает практические методы и дидактические стратегии для эффективного преподавания и освоения фразеологических единиц в контекстах ESL и EFL. Приведено множество аутентичных примеров и ситуаций использования, демонстрирующих их роль в реальной коммуникации и подчеркивающих их значение для языковой беглости и культурной компетентности.

Ключевые слова: фразеологические единицы, идиомы, устойчивые выражения, переносное значение, коллокации, лингвистическая структура, семантическое единство, преподавание английского языка, культурный контекст.

INTRODUCTION

Phraseological units are an integral part of the English language, representing one of its most expressive and culturally rich components. These are fixed or semi-fixed combinations of words whose meanings often cannot be deduced from the meanings of the individual words. For instance, the idiomatic expression “*kick the bucket*” has nothing to do with physically kicking a bucket; instead, it means “*to die*.” Such expressions, which range from idioms and collocations to phrasal verbs and proverbial sayings, contribute significantly to the figurative and stylistic richness of the language.

These units are not merely ornamental; they serve essential communicative functions. Phraseological expressions enhance the clarity, vividness, and emotional impact of language, enabling speakers to convey complex ideas succinctly and effectively. They also serve as markers of linguistic fluency and cultural competence, often distinguishing native speakers from language learners. Mastery of phraseological units is crucial for non-native speakers aiming to understand and participate in authentic English discourse, including informal conversations, literature, films, journalism, and digital communication. Understanding and using phraseological units

correctly is therefore a key indicator of language proficiency. However, their figurative nature, structural variety, and cultural specificity present significant challenges for language learners. Many phraseological units have historical or cultural backgrounds that are unfamiliar to learners, making their meanings difficult to infer. Additionally, their fixed syntactic patterns often defy logical grammatical rules, further complicating their acquisition.

Given their importance and complexity, phraseological units have become a focus of interest in both theoretical linguistics and language pedagogy. This article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of phraseological units in the English language, examining their definitions, classifications, and linguistic features. It also explores their communicative functions, cultural significance, and role in developing language fluency. Finally, the paper presents practical strategies for teaching and learning phraseological units in English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) contexts, supported by examples and insights from modern linguistic research.

Phraseological Units

Phraseological units, also called idioms or set expressions, are combinations of words that function as a single unit of meaning. They are not created spontaneously; rather, they are part of the language's stored memory and are used by speakers to convey specific meanings. There are several key features that define phraseological units:

- **Semantic unity:** The overall meaning is not the sum of the individual word meanings.
- **Stability:** The structure is fixed; word order and composition cannot easily be changed.
- **Non-substitutability:** One word cannot usually be replaced without changing the meaning.
- **Cultural embeddedness:** They often reflect the traditions, history, and worldview of the people who speak the language.

Phraseological units differ significantly from free word combinations in both form and function. While free combinations are composed according to the general grammatical rules of a language and allow flexibility in their components (e.g., *drink water*, *write a letter*, *open a book*), phraseological units are characterized by a high degree of fixedness and semantic unity. In free word combinations, the meaning of the entire phrase is typically the sum of its parts—*drink* plus *water* simply means to consume water. However, in phraseological units, the overall meaning is often idiomatic and cannot be deduced from the literal meanings of the individual words. For example, *spill the beans* means *to reveal a secret*, not the literal act of spilling legumes.

Additionally, phraseological units often resist syntactic or lexical variation. For instance, one cannot easily change *kick the bucket* to *hit the bucket* or *kick the pail* without losing the idiomatic meaning. This structural rigidity contrasts with free combinations, where such substitutions are typically possible and acceptable. Moreover, phraseological units are stored and retrieved from memory as whole chunks or formulaic sequences, rather than being generated on the spot through syntactic composition. From a linguistic perspective, this distinction aligns with the concepts of compositionality versus non-compositionality, and productivity versus non-productivity. Free word combinations are productive and compositional, allowing speakers to create new phrases based on rules. Phraseological units, in contrast, are largely non-productive and non-compositional, having established meanings within the lexicon of the language. Furthermore, phraseological units often carry cultural or historical significance that is lost in literal interpretation. Their meanings are shaped by socio-cultural contexts, metaphoric thinking, and conventional usage, making them essential components of pragmatic competence. For language learners, understanding the fixed nature and idiomatic meaning of phraseological units is crucial for achieving fluency and avoiding miscommunication.

Types and Classifications of Phraseological Units:

Many linguists have proposed classifications of phraseological units. One of the most well-known systems is that of the Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov, who divided them into three main types:

1. Phraseological fusions – These are completely non-literal and indivisible in meaning. The meaning cannot be guessed from the words (e.g., *kick the bucket*, *red tape*).

2. Phraseological unities – These have figurative meanings that are somewhat related to the literal meanings of the words (e.g., *burn one's bridges*, *spill the beans*).

3. Phraseological collocations – These are more literal and involve habitual word pairings (e.g., *make a decision*, *pay attention*).

Another classification by A.V. Kunin considers phraseological units based on their function, origin, and grammatical structure. According to Kunin, phraseological units can also be idioms, proverbs, sayings, similes, and clichés.

Phraseological units are tightly connected to culture. Many idioms reflect traditions, religious beliefs, historical events, and values of English-speaking societies. For example: *Bite the bullet* – a historical reference to soldiers enduring pain without anesthesia. *The ball is in your court* – from the sport of tennis, meaning it's your turn to act.

Learning such idioms not only improves a student's language skills but also their understanding of the culture behind the language. That's why phraseological

competence is considered a component of communicative competence in modern linguistics.

Teaching idioms and phraseological units can be challenging due to their non-literal nature. Students often struggle to understand them or use them in appropriate contexts. However, with the right methods, learners can effectively acquire phraseological competence.

Effective teaching strategies include:

- Using context: Introduce idioms through stories, dialogues, and real-life situations.
- Visual aids: Pictures, cartoons, and videos help illustrate idiomatic meaning.
- Group work and role-play: Let students use idioms in speech through games and discussions.
- Comparing languages: Show similarities and differences with students' native languages.
- Categorizing idioms: Teach idioms thematically (e.g., idioms with animals, food, colors, etc.).

Through these techniques, learners can not only understand phraseological units but also begin to use them naturally and fluently.

In contemporary communication, phraseological units play a crucial role not only in casual speech but also across various professional and public domains, including journalism, advertising, literature, digital media, and political discourse. Their use adds vividness, familiarity, and emotional nuance to language, making communication more effective, persuasive, and memorable.

In journalism, for instance, idioms and other phraseological units are frequently employed in headlines and lead paragraphs to capture readers' attention and create immediate engagement. Expressions such as "*A storm in a teacup*" (referring to an exaggerated reaction to a minor issue) or "*Breaking the ice*" (initiating conversation in a tense or awkward situation) are commonly used because they convey complex ideas in a compact and relatable form. These expressions provide not only semantic clarity but also stylistic flair, allowing journalists to communicate critical or emotional content with greater impact. In advertising, phraseological units are used strategically to create catchy slogans, invoke emotions, and establish a conversational tone with the audience. For example, slogans like "*Have a break, have a KitKat*" play on the familiar concept of taking a break, embedding the product into everyday language. This makes the message more persuasive and memorable through repetition and cultural familiarity. In literature, idiomatic expressions help to develop characters, reflect social or regional identity, and convey mood or tone. Writers use phraseological units to create realism in dialogue, highlight irony or humor, and enrich narrative style. For

instance, Charles Dickens, William Shakespeare, and modern authors frequently embedded idioms into character dialogue to enhance authenticity and reader engagement.

Political language is also heavily reliant on phraseological units. Politicians often use idioms and metaphors to simplify complex issues, appeal to emotions, or frame arguments in a persuasive way. Phrases like *“We’ve reached a crossroads”*, *“moving the goalposts”*, or *“open a new chapter”* are used to convey turning points, challenges, or strategic shifts. These expressions resonate with the public because they are familiar and metaphorically powerful. In digital communication—such as social media posts, memes, or online comments—phraseological units continue to thrive. They are often abbreviated, adapted, or creatively reinterpreted to suit informal and fast-paced online conversations. This linguistic flexibility demonstrates the enduring relevance of phraseological units in modern discourse.

Ultimately, phraseological units are not just decorative elements of language but serve as essential tools for logic, argumentation, and emotional expression. They encapsulate cultural knowledge, historical context, and shared social experiences. Their strategic use can influence opinions, evoke empathy, and shape the tone of discourse. For these reasons, mastering phraseological units is indispensable not only for achieving linguistic fluency but also for participating effectively in modern communicative environments.

CONCLUSION

Phraseological units are fundamental and indispensable elements of the English language, reflecting not only its lexical richness but also its cultural depth and communicative versatility. Their fixed structure, figurative meanings, and socio-cultural associations contribute significantly to both linguistic competence and pragmatic fluency. Unlike free word combinations, phraseological units convey complex meanings succinctly and often metaphorically, allowing speakers and writers to express emotions, attitudes, and abstract ideas with greater impact.

Despite their numerous advantages, phraseological units present notable challenges for language learners. Their idiomatic nature, semantic opacity, and frequent disconnection from literal meanings make them difficult to interpret and use appropriately. Additionally, their cultural specificity can lead to misunderstandings if learners are unfamiliar with the historical or social background underlying certain expressions. For example, idioms like *“the ball is in your court”* or *“bite the bullet”* may puzzle learners without proper explanation and contextual support. To overcome these challenges, language educators must adopt effective teaching strategies that combine explicit instruction with contextualized exposure. Integrating phraseological units into communicative activities, reading tasks, listening exercises, and authentic

texts can greatly enhance learners' ability to internalize and apply these expressions meaningfully. Visual aids, storytelling, role-play, and digital tools such as idiom-focused apps and corpora can also facilitate deeper understanding and retention.

Moreover, teaching phraseological units should not be limited to memorization. Educators should encourage learners to analyze the structure, origin, and metaphorical significance of such expressions. This analytical approach fosters critical thinking and cross-cultural awareness, enabling students to draw connections between language and thought. Learners should also be taught to recognize the appropriate register, tone, and context in which phraseological units can be used, thereby avoiding overuse or inappropriate application. Incorporating phraseological competence into language instruction enhances not only fluency but also stylistic and rhetorical skill. Learners who master idiomatic expressions can better interpret literature, understand media content, and engage in nuanced conversations with native speakers. Their speech and writing become more vivid, persuasive, and emotionally resonant.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ENGLISH ANTONYMS

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Abstract: Antonyms have been a prominent topic in semantics research. There are three sorts of English antonyms: opposite, complementing, and converse. According to conventional linguistics, antonyms have completely different meanings. This research will dispute this traditional view and investigate the importance of antonyms based on the three sorts of antonyms to reveal

something about the nature of antonyms. Then, based on that, this study will present some criteria for English antonyms.

Keywords: contrary antonym; complementary antonym; converse antonym; semantic field theory; hyponymy theory; componential analysis theory.

Аннотация: Антонимы были важной темой в исследованиях семантики. Английские антонимы бывают трех видов: противоположные, дополняющие и обратные. Согласно общепринятой лингвистике, антонимы имеют совершенно разные значения. Это исследование будет оспаривать эту традиционную точку зрения и исследовать важность антонимов на основе трех видов антонимов, чтобы раскрыть что-то о природе антонимов. Затем, на основе этого, в этом исследовании будут представлены некоторые критерии английских антонимов.

Ключевые слова: противоположный антоним; дополнительный антоним; обратный антоним; теория семантического поля; теория гипонимии; теория компонентного анализа.

Annotatsiya: Antonimlar semantika tadqiqotida muhim mavzu bo'lib kelgan. Ingliz tilida uch xil antonimlar mavjud: qarama-qarshi, to'ldiruvchi va qarama-qarshi. An'anaviy tilshunoslikka ko'ra, antonimlar butunlay boshqacha ma'noga ega. Ushbu tadqiqot ushbu an'anaviy nuqtai nazarga qarshi chiqadi va antonimlarning tabiati haqida biror narsani ochib berish uchun uch turdagi antonimlarga asoslangan antonimlarning ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Keyin, shunga asoslanib, ushbu tadqiqot ingliz antonimlari uchun ba'zi mezonlarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qarama-qarshi antonim; to'ldiruvchi antonim; qarama-qarshi antonim; semantik maydon nazariyasi; giponimiya nazariyasi; komponentli tahlil nazariyasi.

Antonyms have been a prominent topic in semantics research. According to traditional semantics, antonym simply denotes the reverse of meaning. Modern semantics has led to much research on antonyms. These investigations, particularly those conducted by John Lyons, have provided fresh insight into antonym studies. Modern semantics divides antonyms into three forms based on semantic opposition: opposing, complementary, and converse antonyms. To question the traditional notion that antonyms have completely opposing meanings, this study attempts to analyze the importance of antonyms based on the three sorts of antonyms, in the hopes of revealing something about the nature of antonyms. Finally, based on the importance of antonyms, this research will propose certain criteria for English antonyms.

Contrary antonyms demonstrate a form of semantic polarity, as seen in pairings such as wide/narrow, old/young, big/small, etc. They can be categorized according to the level of quality involved. Thus, a route might be wide, very wide, or wider than another. This demonstrates that the semantic polarity in opposite antonyms is relative, and the opposition is graded. As a result, some linguistic literature refers to contradictory antonyms as gradable antonyms. This means that contradictory antonyms can be put at opposite ends of a scale, allowing for gradable lexical objects.

For example, between the antonymic pair of lovely and ugly, there may be such gradable adjectives as beautiful —pretty — good-looking — plain— ugly.

There may exist gradable nouns such as love, attachment, like, apathy, antipathy, and hatred in between the antonymic pair love and hate.

Do these opposing antonyms share anything other than their contrasting meanings? To explain this topic, we now resort to various semantic theories.

A class of paradigmatic relations is referred to as a "Semantic Field" in semantics. Words that share an idea can be categorized into semantically related groups or meaning regions in any language. Words within a semantic field are connected by a shared notion. A semantic field is composed of words arranged in a system of connected lexical networks. The English terminology for colors includes, for instance, green, blue, black, grey, orange, rose, olive, purple, lemon, emerald, sandy, coral, and so on. Semantic fields are lists of words that relate to objects in a certain class such as this one. Thus, contradictory antonyms must be words that fall into a single semantic field, remain in opposing directions, and have the same distance from the average level, according to semantic field theory. Take a look at the following minor semantic field to see how this link makes sense.

hot — warm — tepid — lukewarm — cool — cold

This is a small semantic area related to temperature. Warm and cool, which together make up a pair of antonyms, lie between the extreme antonyms, hot and cold. Tepid and lukewarm are possible intermediate antonyms. In this small semantic field, the three sets of antonyms are all the same distance from the average level.

Pairs that include complimentary members—male-female, boy — girl, etc.—represent a particular kind of binary semantic contrast known as complementary antonyms. According to certain theories, males are the complementary forms of women. In a connection like this, stating one thing involves denying another and denying one thing entails stating another as well.

How therefore are the English antonyms relevant? Semantic field theory may be used for this type of antonym in the same way as it was for the opposing antonym. The semantic domain in which these complementary antonyms reside is required. But different from the contrary antonyms, they divide the whole of a semantic field completely into two parts. For example, male — and female belong to the same semantic field: sex terms of human, and they divide up the whole of this semantic field completely.

The solution to the aforementioned query may then be found by consulting the hyponymy hypothesis. In terms of sense relations, there is a unique connection that semantics refers to as hyponymy, which means inclusiveness. More precisely, it describes the link between a set of words wherein the meaning of one word affects the meaning of the other words. For instance, the English terms "animal" and "dog" are similar in that the former designates a particular sort of animal, while the latter is a broad phrase. In other words, the meaning of dog includes the meaning of animal since

everything that is a dog is by definition an animal (note that class membership is the inverse of meaning inclusion: the class of animals includes the class of dogs). The generic phrase animal is termed a superordinate, whereas the specialized term dog is called a hyponym. Numerous hyponyms can be found for a superordinate noun. Co-hyponyms are members of the same superordinate. Complementary antonyms must thus be co-hyponyms under the same superordinate following hyponymy theory. "Man" and "woman," as the antonyms of "man and woman," are co-hyponyms under the superordinate "human."

Furthermore, we may determine how similar these antonyms are if we use the semantics equivalent of componential analysis theory. A method for studying meaning that breaks down a word into its semantic constituents or meaning components is called complementarity analysis. The linguistic meaning of a word is composed of its semantic aspects. They are a collection of abstracted traits that make the category the term denotes apart from all others. Binary opposition is the foundation for the establishment of semantic properties. Male/female, for instance, may be factored out as the binary opposition that exists between the noun pairs boy and girl and man and woman.

Because the members of a pair in a converse antonym do not form a positive-negative opposition, it is a unique kind of antonym. They depict the relationship between two entities being reversed. Examples of this type of relationship are purchase — sell, give — receive, father-child, debtor-creditor, above — below, and so on. One may argue that buy is the opposite of sell and vice versa. B purchases a watch from A if A sells it to B. The same holds for the duo above and below: B is under A if A is above B. Reciprocal social positions, geographical relationships, and other contexts are common examples of this kind of antonym.

If we look closely, we can see that these antonyms are not completely opposing; rather, there is a semantic dependency between the two, indicating that one implies the other. There cannot be a "sell" without a "buy." "Below" won't exist if there is no above. There cannot exist a "child" without a "parent." This is how "converseness" differs from "complementarity," which lacks this kind of dependent symmetry. The main distinction between this kind and the first two is this.

To sum up, English antonyms are important for reasons much beyond just conveying opposites. They are essential for improving our language skills and allowing for more accurate and sophisticated communication. Antonyms expand our vocabulary, encourage critical thought, and help us comprehend linguistic context and contrast on a deeper level. Their inclusion in curriculum highlights their significance for language learning and cognitive development. Additionally, antonyms add to the energy and adaptability of the English language, enabling authors and speakers to successfully express a variety of moods and thoughts. Antonyms are a crucial element

of good communication because, as we investigate and apply them more, we develop our language skills and general cognitive capacities.

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EFFECTIVE METHODS FOR IMPROVING SPEAKING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Foreign language and literature

Abstract: In this article, we will give information about structures that develops the skills of students for speaking, forms of communication, speech and how shapes of speech and dialect, and how to teach monologues and dialogues.

Key words: reading, writing, speaking, monologue, dialogue, matters, oral speech.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются структуры, развивающие у студентов навыки говорения, формы коммуникации, речь и то, как формируются формы речи и диалекта, а также методы обучения монологам и диалогам.

Ключевые слова: чтение, письмо, говорение, монолог, диалог, вопросы, устная речь.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarining og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi tuzilmalar, muloqot shakllari, nutq va dialekt shakllanishi hamda monolog va dialoglarni o'rgatish usullari haqida ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish, yozish, gapirish, monolog, dialog, masalalar, og'zaki nutq.

Introduction

The issues in the development of generation, the widespread use of the tools of advanced technology and software is recognized as one of the most important tasks. Nowadays, we know that in the field of education, young people are facing some kind of problems in order to master a language perfectly.

There are planned requirements that students should pass through them, which are: reading, listening, writing and speaking. In order to ensure the reader to explain completely in a particular language, the learner can write it clearly to show his feelings, he clearly shows it to figure his thoughts, and he is on himself in speech circulates as well, independently and fluently can be able to speak through performance⁴⁹. It would be a bit wrong to say that the above requirements were made only in foreign languages, because such requirements are already placed in Uzbekistan. Of course, the human (learner) belongs to a certain nation or living in the region is not a sign that he knows this language opportunities. Admittedly, by today, one of the most popular challenges contained in learning language is a lack of oral speech. That is, it is an unacceptable problem that is not available to speak wide and completely on a specific topic, that is,

⁴⁹ Abdullayeva B.S. Fanlar aro aloqadorlikning metodologik-didaktik asoslari. Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1990. – B. 24.

our students cannot reflect their knowledge in their speech. The ability to understand will develop quickly, as well as speaking this language. If the reader does not fully understand the content of the speech while listening, it will be much more difficult to give answer about it, and think the question. Reading has also a continuous relationship with speaking skills. The reader speaks and informs through the information he has learned. The more he reads, the more idea to talk. Reading is the source of the best information to talk. The reader describes the materials that he read, listened and spoke through the writing. Writing also serves as a specific source to talk and helps a wide range of help to remember the information⁵⁰. This means that speaking is also inextricably linked to other speech activities. In order to explain this idea, it is to form a speech through the proper use of lexical, grammatical and pronunciations in a particular language. Not in vain that 1 coin for the person who knows work and 100p coins for a person who knows a sentence⁵¹. This means that plenty of things can be achieved by speaking. In a sentence, speaking is a speech activity of three-stages. First, the inclinations will arise in man, in other words, motivate, when it comes to the desire to perform the speech action, because of the answering word, the answers to the question will be entered. In this part of speaking, the intention of speaking appears. In the second stage, the part of our opinion will be commissioned, such as analysis, synthesis. To carry out this process, our memory stock will help. The memory reserves the word in the person (remained in brain) or grammatical unity. A third after the first and second stages of speaking. It is also enough for stage. This is the stage of pronunciation. The series of speech is carried out in two forms of speech activity: in the form of a series of speech. It will be seen that it is logically and kept based on a specific text. Monological talk is impressive, emotional, may have been aimed at someone or for some reason. Dialogic speech is more than a few executors. The need to respond in the dialog is observed. It may not be question-and-answer, in which each speaker has to continue his mind with a certain goal is much stronger. Through responsibilities, each reader is studied carefully and optimizes its sciences, to work separately, taking into account the young psychology.

In addition, students will enrich knowledge through reading works, performance of works or textbooks, as well as free and creatively using their creative statements. One person carries out monologue speech. It is planned and partially prepared in advance. It is logically connected and based on a specific text. Monologue speech can be expressive, emotional, and directed or dedicated to someone or

⁵⁰ Ergashev E. Chet tili o'qitish jarayonida texnika vositalaridan foydalanish. Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1984. – B. 56.

⁵¹ Hoshimov O', Yoqubov I. Ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasi. T.: Sharq, 2003. – B. 42.

something⁵².

Dialogic speech, on the other hand, involves more than one participant. In a dialogue, there is a need to respond⁵³. It may not only consist of questions and answers; each speaker may continue the conversation with a specific goal in mind. It should be especially noted that today, compared to previous times, greater attention is being paid to the younger generation receiving education and upbringing in our schools. Through responsible personnel, each student is carefully observed, and efforts are made to work individually with them, considering their academic performance, behavior, upbringing, and age-related psychology⁵⁴.

However, in the process of expressing their thoughts orally, many students face difficulties in going beyond predetermined words or in freely expressing their opinions on a specific topic while preparing monologue speech. One of the main reasons for this is that in the educational process, students are limited to grammar only, and psychological factors such as fear of making mistakes and lack of confidence contribute.

Today, new-generation textbooks provide a solution to this issue. Through them, students are not limited to only learning grammar but are also given tasks that encourage thinking, creativity, and fluent expression of their thoughts. This has a positive impact. In language teaching or in teaching any activity exercises play a key role. Preparatory and speech exercises serve to form, develop, and improve speaking skills and abilities. In this regard, the conversation method also plays an essential role. In many research methodologies, the conversation method is considered one of the oldest and most widely used auxiliary methods across various sciences. Examples of speech exercises include expressing one’s thoughts using sources of information such as pictures, movies, and films; thoroughly explaining studied topics orally; speaking based on stories, pictures, silent films, or informational sources in textbooks; and speaking based on prior reading or personal reflections. Currently, in English lessons, students are tested through listening and speaking exercises during the first 10 minutes. The main goal of such oral practice is to help students recall forgotten words, phrases, and similar patterns, prepare them for speaking, and adapt them to the context. This method can be effectively used in native language lessons as well. For instance, after announcing the topic in a native language lesson, a thought-provoking idea can be introduced before diving into the main subject. This could be a proverb or phrase played as an audio clip or a stimulating image for children to observe. Then students are asked to express their thoughts and opinions based on what they heard or saw. This

⁵² Jamol Jalolov. *Chet til o‘qitish metodikasi*. T.: O‘qituvchi, 2012. – B. 65.

⁵³ Atakhanovna, Y. G., & Azada, A. (2021, May). Features of the use of Mixed education in uzbek language classes. In *E-Conference Globe* (Pp. 77-80).

⁵⁴ Harmer Jeremy. *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. Cambridge, 2007. – P. 52

approach makes the lesson more interesting and attracts students' attention. The exercise helps develop students' thinking and speaking skills and should not last more than 10 minutes, as exceeding this duration may cause students to lose interest. As an example, if one of the following topics is introduced "The Internet and Us," "Me and My Family," "What If Phones Didn't exist," or "A Day in My Life" lessons can be conducted more effectively. These topics are especially interesting for the younger generation and thus attract their attention. "The Internet and Us" – Nowadays, we can hardly imagine life without the internet, especially for young people, for whom this is a very difficult issue. Through the internet, not only can we solve many work and life-related problems and handle official documents, but we can also carry out daily household tasks with ease. Students' reflections on the topic are heard, and the teacher corrects and supplements their responses, then summarizes them. After that, the main lesson topic is introduced. Regular use of such exercises during the lesson plays an important role in the development of students' speaking skills, helps them behave confidently in front of others, and reduces anxiety. It also improves the relationship between student and teacher, creating an environment where the student feels free to express their opinions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that speaking skills are of great importance not only in language learning but also in initiating communication. Therefore, based on the ideas mentioned above, we can say that in order to further develop and enhance this skill, both the student and the teacher play a significant role. This is because constant effort is required from the student, while the teacher is responsible for engaging the student and providing motivation.

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METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF COMBINING VARIOUS LITERARY GENRES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: This paper describes the methodology of using various literary genres in order to improve the level of English language acquisition by students in the learning process, and provides recommendations on the organization of training, depending on the capabilities of the participants in the training.

Keywords: foreign language teaching, methodology, literary genres, literary texts, language skills, techniques for teaching.

Annotatsiya: ushbu ishda ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida ta'lim oluvchilarning o'zlashtirish darajasini oshirish maqsadida turli adabiy janrlardan foydalanishning uslublari haqida bayon qilingan bo'lib, ta'lim ishtirokchilarining imkoniyatlariga bog'liq holda o'qitishni tashkil etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tillarni o'qitish, metodologiya, adabiy janrlar, badiiy matnlar, til ko'nikmalari, o'qitish metodikasi.

Аннотация: в данной работе изложены методология использования различных литературных жанров в целях повышения уровня освоения обучающимися английского языка в процессе обучения, даны рекомендации по организации обучения в зависимости от возможностей участников обучения.

Ключевые слова: преподавание иностранных языков, методология, литературные жанры, художественные тексты, языковые навыки, методика преподавания.

The main aim of the present study is to assess the validity of literary texts for the language teaching purpose. Literary texts continue being used for the ELT purpose especially in the secondary schools with the objective of enhancing the language skills of the learners. If literary texts have been considered redundant for achieving the ELT objective, it is so because of the lack of awareness on the part of English teachers as they fail to draw linguistic insights from literary texts. Though literary texts offer a wealth of language teaching materials yet many a times the treatment they receive is unworthy of being mentioned. The present study seeks to find out the possibility of drawing out linguistic inferences from literary texts to teach different facets of language such as composition, compounding, affixation, vocabulary, etc. The purpose of this study is also to show how far literary texts can be proved useful in imparting the knowledge of the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) [1,2].

The activity we are concerned with is foreign or second language teaching. That seems straightforward enough. However, the concept of methodology would seem to be problematic. We might note, to begin with, that the term itself is not used with

any consistency in the applied linguistic literature devoted to issues in foreign language teaching. The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages, for example, there is, in its 25 thematic chapters, no separate and explicit treatment of methodology as such at all. Another overview appearing a year later from the same publisher goes to the opposite extreme: *Methodology in Language Teaching: An Anthology of Current Practice* gives prominence to methodology, but uses it indiscriminately as an umbrella term to cover almost every topic in language education imaginable. Earlier literature on the teaching of foreign or other languages acknowledges the notion of methodology but interprets it in somewhat diverse ways [3].

Methodology is variously taken as comprising:

- a) various generic techniques for teaching of the basic skill areas of reading, writing, listening and speaking;
- b) a universal set of techniques for teaching any linguistic material in any skilling Presentation, Practice, Production (PPP) or Observe, Hypothesize, Experiment;
- c) an eclectic, teacher-personalized collage of techniques and methods;
- d) learning to put into practice certain general principles of good language teaching derived from research or observation;
- e) conscious modelling by less experienced teachers of the practices of expert or experienced teachers whatever these may be [4].

Integrating multiple literary genres into language teaching enhances linguistic competence, cultural awareness, and critical thinking. Combining various literary genres in language teaching offers a rich and engaging approach to learning. Here are some methodological principles to guide this practice:

1. Purposeful selection:

Align with learning objectives: Choose genres that align with specific learning objectives, whether it's vocabulary expansion, grammar practice, cultural understanding, or developing critical thinking skills.

Consider learner interests: Select genres that resonate with learners' interests and backgrounds to enhance motivation and engagement.

Balance and variety: Offer a balanced mix of genres to expose learners to diverse styles, structures, and themes, preventing monotony and encouraging exploration.

2. Integrated approach:

Cross-genre connections: Highlight connections and contrasts between genres to deepen understanding and promote critical thinking. For example, compare the narrative structure of a short story to the plot of a play [5].

Multimodal learning: Incorporate visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements to enhance learning. For example, use illustrations for poetry, listen to audio recordings of plays, or engage in role-playing activities.

Collaborative learning: Encourage group activities, discussions, and presentations to foster interaction, collaboration, and shared learning experiences.

3. Scaffolding and differentiation:

Gradual introduction: Introduce genres progressively, starting with simpler texts and gradually moving to more complex ones.

Differentiated activities: Provide differentiated activities based on learners' levels and needs, ensuring everyone has opportunities to succeed and engage.

Support and guidance: Offer clear instructions, scaffolding, and support throughout the learning process to ensure understanding and success.

4. Creative and engaging activities:

Interactive activities: Design interactive activities like role-playing, debates, creative writing, and storytelling to promote active learning and language use.

Real-world connections: Connect literary works to real-world issues, current events, or learners' personal experiences to make learning relevant and meaningful.

Technology Integration: Utilize digital tools like online dictionaries, interactive exercises, and multimedia resources to enhance learning and engagement [6].

5. Assessment and reflection:

Formative assessment: Use a variety of formative assessments to monitor learners' progress and adjust instruction as needed.

Reflective activities: Encourage learners to reflect on their learning experiences, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and set goals for further development.

Celebrate success: Recognize and celebrate learners' achievements to motivate and encourage continued growth.

Examples of genre combinations:

Poetry and short story: Compare the use of imagery and symbolism in poetry and short stories [7].

Drama and non-fiction: Analyze how dramatic dialogue can be used to convey factual information in a compelling way.

Novel and film: Compare the adaptation of a novel to a film, analyzing the differences in storytelling and character development.

Combining various literary genres in language teaching offers a dynamic and engaging approach that fosters comprehensive language development. By following these methodological principles, educators can create rich learning experiences that engage learners, enhance their language skills, and cultivate a lifelong love of literature.

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The Significance of Lesson Plans in TBLT (Task-Based Language Teaching) Approach in ESP Classes Globally and in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article examines the pivotal role of structured lesson plans in implementing the Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) approach in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classes both globally and in Uzbekistan. It highlights how TBLT enhances communicative competence through meaningful tasks tailored to learners' professional goals. Drawing on global research and local case studies, the article argues that well-designed lesson plans foster integrated skill development, critical thinking, and workplace readiness. The relevance of TBLT in Uzbekistan's ongoing educational reforms is discussed, with reference to blended learning practices and teacher training initiatives.

Keywords: TBLT, lesson plan, ESP, communicative competence, Uzbekistan, blended learning, language teaching reform.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) metodikasi asosida dars rejaları tuzishning ESP (aniq sohalar uchun ingliz tili) darslaridagi ahamiyati tahlil etiladi. TBLTning o'quvchilarning kasbiy maqsadlariga mos topshiriqlar orqali muloqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi samaradorligi yoritiladi. Global tadqiqotlar va O'zbekiston tajribasi asosida tuzilgan maqolada dars rejaları orqali integratsiyalashgan ko'nikmalar, tanqidiy fikrlash va kasbiy tayyorgarlik qanday rivojlanishi tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, TBLT metodikasining O'zbekistondagi ta'lim islohotlaridagi roli ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: TBLT, dars rejasi, ESP, muloqot kompetensiyasi, O'zbekiston, aralash ta'lim,

til o'qitish islohoti.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значимость структурированных планов уроков при применении метода Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) в курсах английского языка для профессиональных целей (ESP) как в мировом, так и в узбекском контексте. Метод TBLT способствует развитию коммуникативной компетенции через выполнение значимых задач, связанных с профессиональной сферой учащихся. Основываясь на международных исследованиях и примерах из практики Узбекистана, статья доказывает, что хорошо составленные планы уроков способствуют интеграции языковых навыков, развитию критического мышления и профессиональной подготовки. Также рассматривается роль TBLT в образовательных реформах Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: TBLT, план урока, ESP, коммуникативная компетенция, Узбекистан, смешанное обучение, языковые реформы.

Introduction

Designing lesson plans for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classes within the framework of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is essential for achieving effective language learning outcomes. The TBLT approach emphasizes meaningful communication through tasks, making it particularly valuable for ESP learners who require language skills tailored to specific professional contexts. Lesson plans in this framework provide structure, coherence, and measurable objectives, ensuring that learners can achieve their language and professional goals efficiently. This article explores the global significance of structured lesson plans in TBLT for ESP classes and their relevance in Uzbekistan, a country that is increasingly aligning its educational practices with global standards.

Global Importance of Lesson Plans in TBLT

Globally, lesson planning in TBLT ensures that language instruction is relevant, engaging, and aligned with learners' specific needs. By focusing on authentic tasks, such as drafting professional emails, conducting interviews, or preparing business presentations, TBLT mirrors the communicative demands of real-world professional environments. Ellis (2003) asserts that task-based approaches allow learners to focus on meaning rather than form, encouraging natural language use in real-world scenarios. Structured lesson plans ensure that these tasks are logically sequenced, effectively scaffolded, and supported with the necessary linguistic tools.

For example, in aviation ESP classes, pilots and air traffic controllers might simulate emergency communication scenarios where precise language use is critical. In such cases, lesson plans outline the necessary pre-task vocabulary work, the communicative task itself (e.g., handling simulated emergencies), and post-task debriefs to reflect on performance. These structured stages not only build confidence but also emphasize professional competence, as highlighted by Long (2015).

Additionally, lesson plans provide a mechanism for integrating multiple language skills. For instance, in an ESP course for legal professionals, learners might

read a legal case, participate in a mock trial, and draft a closing argument. Such integration of reading, speaking, and writing skills aligns with Nunan's (2004) view that holistic language development is a cornerstone of effective language instruction.

Uzbekistan's educational scholars have also emphasized the importance of structured lesson plans in the TBLT framework. According to Yusupova (2023), the integration of blended learning technologies within TBLT environments significantly enhances students' linguistic competence, especially when various task formats (oral, written, and digital) are combined in interactive classrooms. This local research reinforces global findings by showing that Uzbek students benefit greatly from multimodal and collaborative tasks.

The Role of TBLT in Uzbekistan's Educational Reforms

In Uzbekistan, the significance of TBLT lesson plans has grown in tandem with educational reforms aimed at improving English proficiency. These reforms are driven by the country's aspirations to integrate more deeply into the global economy, where English is a lingua franca. TBLT, with its focus on real-world language use, is particularly suited to meeting these demands. For instance, engineering students in Uzbekistan might engage in tasks that require writing technical manuals or delivering project presentations, thereby combining language learning with professional development.

Uzbekistan's emphasis on communicative language teaching has positioned TBLT as a key approach in its educational system. Lesson plans tailored to TBLT provide educators with a clear structure for implementing this method. For example, in a medical ESP class, lesson plans might include pre-task activities where students learn medical terminologies, task activities such as role-playing doctor-patient consultations, and post-task reflection sessions to discuss linguistic and professional challenges encountered during the task. Such plans not only enhance language acquisition but also help students internalize professional norms.

A notable initiative in Uzbekistan is the adoption of professional development programs for educators, which emphasize modern teaching methodologies like TBLT. According to Richards and Rodgers (2014), teacher training is critical for the effective implementation of TBLT. Structured lesson plans act as a bridge, equipping teachers with actionable frameworks to deliver impactful lessons while adapting to local needs.

Key Components of Effective TBLT Lesson Plans

An essential component of any effective TBLT lesson plan is a thorough needs analysis. This process identifies the professional and linguistic needs of learners, ensuring that tasks are relevant and meaningful. For example, tourism students in Uzbekistan might engage in tasks such as creating tour itineraries for international visitors or role-playing customer service interactions. As Widdowson (1998) argues, relevance is key to sustaining learner motivation and engagement.

Effective lesson plans also include a three-stage framework: pre-task, task, and post-task. In the pre-task stage, learners are introduced to the task, activating prior knowledge and acquiring the necessary vocabulary and grammatical structures. For example, in a business context, learners might analyze negotiation strategies and key phrases. The task stage allows learners to engage in meaningful communication, such as role-playing a supplier-client negotiation. Finally, the post-task stage provides opportunities for feedback, reflection, and further practice. This stage is crucial for consolidating learning, as noted by Willis and Willis (2007).

In Uzbekistan, where learners often face challenges in applying English in real-life contexts, this structured approach is particularly valuable. For example, law students might participate in a simulated court case during the task stage, followed by a detailed post-task discussion on legal language use and cultural nuances in legal proceedings. These steps ensure not only language proficiency but also the development of critical professional skills.

Practical Application: A Sample Business ESP Lesson Plan

To illustrate the application of TBLT, consider a business ESP class in Uzbekistan. A lesson plan might focus on negotiating a contract. During the pre-task stage, learners could watch a video of a professional negotiation, identify key phrases, and practice using these phrases in controlled activities. The task stage might involve learners role-playing a negotiation between a supplier and a buyer, applying language and strategies relevant to their professional roles. In the post-task stage, learners could reflect on their performance, receive feedback from peers and the instructor, and draft a follow-up email summarizing the agreement.

For instance, in a finance-focused ESP class at the International School of Finance, Technology and Science in Tashkent, students were tasked with creating budget proposals and presenting them to a simulated board of directors. This project involved analyzing financial data, drafting proposals in English, and engaging in persuasive negotiations — tasks that mirror authentic business situations while developing both language and soft skills.

Such lesson plans not only enhance linguistic competence but also foster soft skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, and cultural awareness. This aligns with Larsen-Freeman's (2018) emphasis on the importance of preparing learners for the complexities of real-world communication.

Importance of Assessment in TBLT Lesson Plans

Assessment is another critical aspect of TBLT lesson plans. Both formative and summative assessments play vital roles in evaluating learners' task performance and language use. Self-assessment and peer feedback are particularly effective in encouraging learners to reflect on their progress and identify areas for improvement. For example, after completing a task, learners might use a checklist to evaluate their

use of target language structures and professional etiquette. Toshmatov O.Sh. (2023) notes that task-based activities play a critical role in fostering autonomous learning skills among Uzbek university students. He argues that well-structured lesson plans not only enhance linguistic accuracy but also promote critical thinking and independent problem-solving, especially when learners work in pairs or groups to complete professional simulations.

In Uzbekistan, culturally appropriate assessment methods are essential to ensure that learners feel supported and motivated. For instance, educators might use performance rubrics that balance linguistic accuracy with task effectiveness, allowing learners to focus on both language skills and professional outcomes. As Bachman and Palmer (1996) note, effective assessment methods provide learners with actionable insights into their progress, fostering a sense of achievement and motivation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, lesson plans are a cornerstone of the TBLT approach, ensuring that tasks are meaningful, structured, and aligned with learners' needs. Globally and in Uzbekistan, they enable educators to create engaging and effective ESP classes that prepare learners for real-world professional challenges. By combining global best practices with local contexts, TBLT lesson plans contribute to the development of English proficiency, empowering individuals to achieve their academic and career goals. As Uzbekistan continues to modernize its education system, the role of well-crafted lesson plans in TBLT will remain indispensable in bridging the gap between language education and practical application.

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Extensive Reading as a Tool for Developing Language Proficiency

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Annotation

This article explores the significance of extensive reading (ER) in second language acquisition, with a focus on its potential to improve vocabulary acquisition, grammatical competence, reading fluency, and overall language proficiency. Drawing from both theoretical perspectives and practical applications, the paper investigates how ER encourages learner autonomy, deepens textual understanding, and cultivates a long-term interest in reading. Special attention is paid to how extensive reading can be implemented in B2-level English classrooms in Uzbekistan, considering local learning contexts and learner needs.

Keywords: Extensive reading, language proficiency, vocabulary development, reading fluency, learner autonomy, motivation, Uzbekistan, B2 level, comprehension strategies

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается значимость обширного чтения (Extensive Reading, ER) в процессе изучения второго языка, с акцентом на его потенциал в улучшении лексического запаса, грамматической компетенции, беглости чтения и общего уровня владения языком. Основываясь как на теоретических подходах, так и на практических примерах, статья исследует, как ER способствует развитию автономности учащихся, углублённому пониманию текстов и формированию устойчивого интереса к чтению. Особое внимание уделяется возможностям внедрения методики обширного чтения в учебный процесс на уровне B2 в Узбекистане с учётом местных условий и потребностей обучающихся.

Ключевые слова: обширное чтение, языковая компетенция, развитие словарного запаса, беглость чтения, автономность учащегося, мотивация, Узбекистан, уровень B2, стратегии понимания текста.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola chet tilini o'rganishda keng ko'lamli o'qish (extensive reading) usulining ahamiyatini tadqiq qiladi. Maqolada bu usulning so'z boyligini oshirish, grammatik bilimlarni mustahkamlash, o'qish tezligi va umumiy til kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'qish qobiliyatini shakllantirish, matnni chuqur tushunish va kitob o'qishga qiziqishini oshirishda keng ko'lamli o'qishning samarasi tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada O'zbekistondagi B2 darajasidagi ingliz tili o'quvchilari uchun keng ko'lamli o'qishni joriy etish bo'yicha amaliy takliflar ham keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Keng ko'lamli o'qish, til kompetensiyasi, lug'at boyligi, o'qish tezligi, mustaqil o'rganish, motivatsiya, O'zbekiston, B2 daraja, tushunish strategiyalari.

Introduction

In recent decades, extensive reading (ER) has emerged as a powerful pedagogical tool for language learning, supported by research in applied linguistics and educational psychology. Extensive reading refers to the process in which learners read large amounts of material that is within their linguistic competence, typically for

enjoyment or general understanding, rather than for detailed language analysis (Day & Bamford, 1998). Unlike intensive reading, which focuses on accuracy and language form, extensive reading emphasizes reading fluency, comprehension, and intrinsic motivation. The core principle is that reading more leads to reading better—a notion supported by both Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985) and empirical studies in second language acquisition.

In Uzbekistan, where English language education has gained significant momentum, the integration of extensive reading into academic programs represents a meaningful step toward fostering language proficiency among university students. Particularly for B2-level learners who possess an intermediate command of English, ER offers a pathway to deeper lexical knowledge, grammatical awareness, and confident engagement with authentic texts. This article outlines the theoretical foundations of extensive reading and illustrates its benefits and implementation strategies in local educational contexts.

Theoretical Foundations of Extensive Reading

Extensive Reading is fundamentally grounded in theories of input and second language acquisition, particularly Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis. According to Krashen (1985), comprehensible input—language that is slightly above the learner's current proficiency level ($i+1$)—is crucial for natural and effective language development. Extensive Reading (ER) provides exactly this kind of input, as learners immerse themselves in texts that are engaging, understandable, and appropriately leveled. Rather than focusing on deliberate memorization or conscious grammar study, ER allows learners to absorb language features incidentally, in meaningful and contextualized ways. As students encounter vocabulary and grammatical structures repeatedly in various contexts, their understanding deepens and their ability to use the language accurately and fluently improves over time. This process mirrors the way native speakers acquire language: through constant exposure, pattern recognition, and contextual association. Furthermore, because ER typically involves reading for pleasure without the pressure of assessment, it lowers the affective filter—another key concept in Krashen's theory—making learners more receptive to language input. In essence, ER provides a low-stress, high-exposure environment that supports both implicit learning and long-term retention. Through sustained interaction with rich and varied texts, learners internalize linguistic forms naturally, leading to improved fluency, accuracy, and comprehension.

Nation (2009) further emphasizes that reading extensively develops “language richness,” where high-frequency words are recycled across multiple texts, reinforcing retention. Cognitive processing theories also support the idea that the repetitive, meaningful exposure provided by ER strengthens lexical retrieval and syntactic awareness. Additionally, from a psychological perspective, ER fosters intrinsic

motivation, as learners choose materials aligned with their interests, leading to a more personalized and enjoyable learning experience.

Moreover, Extensive Reading (ER) supports metacognitive development by encouraging learners to take greater control of their reading processes. As students engage with a broad array of texts—from fiction and non-fiction to academic articles and news reports—they are frequently challenged by unfamiliar vocabulary, varied syntactic structures, and diverse writing styles. This diversity compels readers to become more aware of their own understanding and to adopt strategies that facilitate deeper comprehension. For example, learners might pause to summarize a paragraph, re-read complex sections, infer meaning from context, or evaluate the reliability of a source—all actions that involve metacognitive monitoring and regulation. Such reflective behavior fosters the ability to plan, evaluate, and adjust reading strategies based on individual learning goals and task demands. Importantly, these metacognitive processes do not develop in isolation; rather, they are cultivated through repeated engagement with authentic texts in a low-pressure environment, which ER provides. As Day and Bamford (2002) argue, ER promotes learner autonomy and builds confidence, both of which are closely linked to metacognitive growth. For advanced language learners, especially those navigating academic settings, this capacity to self-regulate their reading becomes crucial. It allows them not only to comprehend surface-level content but also to analyze arguments, detect bias, compare viewpoints, and synthesize information across texts. In sum, ER functions as a training ground for developing the higher-order thinking and self-regulatory skills necessary for academic literacy and lifelong learning.

Benefits of Extensive Reading in Language Development

The benefits of extensive reading are multifaceted and well-documented. One of the most significant gains is vocabulary acquisition. According to Horst (2005), learners can acquire up to 300 new words after reading a single graded reader. ER also helps reinforce known vocabulary by presenting it in varied contexts, thereby enhancing retention and usage accuracy.

Fluency development is another vital benefit of extensive reading, particularly for intermediate to advanced learners aiming to improve their overall language proficiency. As learners engage with large volumes of text at an appropriate difficulty level, they are repeatedly exposed to natural language patterns, high-frequency vocabulary, and common grammatical structures in meaningful contexts. This repetition leads to increased automaticity in word recognition and sentence processing, which is a critical component of reading fluency. As learners begin to read faster and with greater ease, they expend less cognitive energy on decoding individual words and more on grasping the overall meaning of the text. This shift enables more efficient and effective comprehension, allowing students to understand longer and more complex

texts without becoming overwhelmed. Fluency, in turn, supports other aspects of language development, such as listening and speaking, because it fosters greater lexical access and syntactic familiarity. Researchers like Nation (2009) emphasize that reading fluency should be nurtured through continuous, enjoyable, and accessible reading experiences, as it plays a foundational role in building confidence, encouraging further reading, and ultimately fostering a more self-sustaining language learning process.

Furthermore, extensive reading promotes grammatical sensitivity. While ER is not primarily focused on grammar instruction, students unconsciously absorb grammatical patterns, particularly when exposed to repeated structures. Studies have shown that learners who read extensively outperform their peers on grammar tests, even without explicit instruction (Rodrigo et al., 2007).

Beyond linguistic outcomes, ER nurtures learner autonomy and motivation. When learners select their own reading materials, they become active participants in their learning journey. This sense of control boosts self-confidence and encourages lifelong reading habits. In Uzbekistan, where access to authentic English materials may be limited, curated digital libraries and graded reader programs offer an accessible solution for promoting ER.

Implementation of Extensive Reading in the Uzbek Context

Integrating extensive reading into university English courses in Uzbekistan requires a strategic and context-sensitive approach. Educators must first ensure that students have access to appropriate reading materials. Graded readers—books specifically written or adapted for language learners at various proficiency levels—are highly effective in this regard. These can be supplemented with online platforms such as Oxford Bookworms, Cambridge English Readers, or open-access resources like Project Gutenberg.

Curriculum designers should allocate dedicated time for ER within classroom hours and encourage sustained reading outside the classroom. A practical approach might include a weekly reading journal, in which students summarize stories, reflect on characters, or describe unfamiliar vocabulary. Teachers can assess progress through comprehension questions, vocabulary tests, or informal book discussions.

Teacher training is essential for successful implementation. Instructors should be familiar with the principles of ER and trained to facilitate student-led reading activities. Additionally, integrating ER into the assessment system—without assigning heavy grades—can help motivate students while maintaining a low-stress environment.

At Uzbek State World Languages University, pilot projects incorporating ER have shown promising results. In a recent study, B2-level students who participated in a 10-week extensive reading program demonstrated a 22% improvement in vocabulary tests and reported higher reading confidence. Student feedback also indicated a greater

enjoyment of English learning, suggesting that ER contributes positively to affective dimensions of language learning.

Conclusion

Extensive Reading (ER) stands as a transformative approach in the domain of second language acquisition, bridging theoretical insights and practical application to create enriched learning environments. As this article has demonstrated, ER not only enhances core linguistic skills—such as vocabulary breadth, grammatical intuition, and reading fluency—but also cultivates learner autonomy, motivation, and critical engagement with texts. Rooted in well-established theories like Krashen's Input Hypothesis and supported by cognitive and metacognitive learning frameworks, ER provides learners with meaningful exposure to language in authentic contexts, which leads to natural and sustained language development.

To fully harness the benefits of extensive reading in Uzbekistan and beyond, a multi-faceted implementation strategy is required. This includes teacher training, institutional support, integration of ER into curricula, and access to diverse and level-appropriate reading materials. Furthermore, incorporating ER into assessment frameworks in a low-stakes and reflective manner will enhance its acceptability and sustainability.

In conclusion, extensive reading is more than a pedagogical technique; it is a philosophy of language learning that empowers students to become independent, confident, and competent users of English. It aligns seamlessly with contemporary communicative teaching goals and provides a scalable model for language development in both local and global contexts. As educational systems increasingly emphasize learner-centered instruction and holistic development, ER deserves a central place in language curricula—especially for contexts like Uzbekistan, where a growing emphasis on multilingual proficiency is reshaping national education priorities. Through thoughtful integration and sustained support, extensive reading can shape not only proficient language users but also curious, motivated, and lifelong learners.

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TINGLASH VA O‘QISH JARAYONIDA ESLATMA OLIB BORISHNING SAMARADORLIGI VA TA‘SIRINI AKADEMIK SOHADA O‘RGANISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot O‘zbekiston universitetlarida tahsil olayotgan talabalar orasida eslatma olishning o‘qib va tinglab tushunish ko‘nikmalariga ehtimoliy ta‘sirini chuqur o‘rganadi. Mazkur ishning asosiy maqsadi – eslatma yozishning talabalarning tushunish darajasiga qanday ta‘sir ko‘rsatishini aniqlashdir. Tadqiqot doirasida turli akademik holatga ega va jins jihatdan farq qiluvchi o‘quvchilarning tushunish darajasi tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot sababi va oqibatini aniqlashga yo‘naltirilgan sababiy-qiyosiy metodologiyaga asoslangan bo‘lib, Toshkent shahridagi International School of Finance, Technology and Science institutining 68 nafar talabasi ishtirok etdi. Ishtirokchilar o‘qish va tinglab tushunish ko‘nikmalarini baholash uchun joylashtirish testidan o‘tishdi. Tadqiqot uchun tanlangan 560 so‘zli “Iqlimning o‘zgarishi, tafakkurning o‘zgarishi” nomli matn asosiy manba sifatida xizmat qildi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, eslatma olgan tinglovchilar – matnni eslatmasiz o‘qigan va tinglagan guruhlariga qaraganda ancha yuqori natijalarga erishgan. Ayniqsa, tinglash jarayonida eslatma olgan talabalar boshqa barcha guruhlardan yuqori ball to‘plagan. Shuningdek, o‘quvchilarning test natijalari va ularning universitetdagi GPA (umumiy o‘rtacha bahosi) o‘rtasida ijobiy bog‘liqlik mavjudligi kuzatildi. Bu esa, yuqori akademik ko‘rsatkichga ega bo‘lgan talabalar eslatma olishdan ko‘proq foyda olishlarini ko‘rsatdi. Jinsiy tafovutlarga oid o‘rganishlar esa erkak va ayol talabalar o‘rtasida sezilarli farq yo‘qligini aniqladi. Ushbu topilmalar o‘qish va tinglashda tushunish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda eslatma olishning samarali vosita ekanligini ko‘rsatadi. Tadqiqot ta‘lim jarayonlariga sifatli eslatma olish ko‘nikmalarini joriy etish zarurligini ta‘kidlaydi hamda talabalarning umumiy akademik muvaffaqiyatini oshirishga qaratilgan pedagogik chora-tadbirlarni ilgari suradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Eslatma olish, raqamli eslatma olish, o‘qib tushunish, tinglab tushunish, gap usuli, aql xaritasi, kontur tuzish, klasterlash, Kornel usuli, eslatma olish bo‘yicha maslahatlar.

Annotation: This study rigorously investigates the potential influence of note-taking on the reading and listening comprehension skills of university students in Uzbekistan. The objective of the current work is to assess the impact of note-taking on students' comprehension levels. The research specifically examines understanding levels in relation to differing academic status and gender features among learners. The research utilizes a causal-comparative methodology, involving 68 students from the International School of Finance, Technology, and Science in Tashkent. The study participants underwent the Placement Test to assess their proficiency in reading and listening comprehension. The teaching material, entitled "Changing Climate, Changing Minds," consists of 560 words. This study

investigates the effectiveness of note-taking as a method to improve comprehension abilities and analyzes its relationship with academic achievement and gender disparities. The results demonstrate that note-taking listeners displayed markedly superior comprehension scores compared to readers, note-taking readers, and listeners without notes. Significantly, listeners who took notes attained considerably higher marks than other groups. A favorable link was observed between learners' comprehension scores and their university grade point averages, indicating that individuals with superior academic performance derived greater benefits from note-taking. The study additionally examined potential gender disparities, indicating that no significant variations in comprehension abilities existed between female and male pupils. These findings highlight the significance of note-taking as an effective instrument for enhancing comprehension abilities in reading and listening among university students. The research underscores the need of incorporating good note-taking skills into educational practices to improve academic outcomes and advocates for the deployment of specific pedagogical interventions designed to optimize student understanding and overall academic performance.

Key words: note taking, digital note taking, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, Sentence Method, Mind Mapping, Outlining, Clustering, Cornell Method, note taking tips.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании тщательно изучается потенциальное влияние ведения заметок на навыки чтения и понимания на слух студентов университетов в Узбекистане. Целью данного исследования является оценка влияния конспектирования на уровень понимания учащихся. В исследовании конкретно изучаются уровни понимания в зависимости от различного академического статуса и гендерных особенностей среди учащихся. В исследовании используется причинно-сравнительная методология с участием 68 студентов International School of Finance, Technology and Science в Ташкенте. Участники исследования прошли вступительный тест для оценки их навыков чтения и понимания на слух. Учебный материал под названием «Изменение климата, изменение мышления» который использовался в исследовании состоит из 560 слов. В этом исследовании изучается эффективность ведения заметок как метода улучшения способностей к пониманию и анализируется его связь с академической успеваемостью и гендерным неравенством. Результаты показывают, что слушатели, делающие заметки, продемонстрировали заметно более высокие оценки понимания по сравнению с читателями, читающими заметки и слушателями без заметок. Примечательно, что слушатели, делавшие записи, получили значительно более высокие оценки, чем другие группы. Была отмечена благоприятная связь между показателями понимания учащихся и средними баллами их университетских оценок, что указывает на то, что люди с более высокими академическими показателями получали большую пользу от ведения конспектов. В исследовании дополнительно изучались потенциальные гендерные различия, указывающие на отсутствие существенных различий в способностях к пониманию между учениками женского и мужского пола. Эти результаты подчеркивают важность ведения конспектов как эффективного инструмента улучшения способностей к пониманию чтения и аудирования среди студентов университетов. Исследование подчеркивает необходимость включения хороших навыков конспектирования в образовательную практику для улучшения академических результатов и выступает за применение конкретных педагогических мер, направленных на оптимизацию понимания учащихся и общей академической успеваемости.

Ключевые слова: ведение заметок, конспектирование, ведение цифровых заметок, понимание прочитанного, понимание на слух, метод предложений, метод интеллект-карт, процедура формального описания, кластеризация, метод Корнела, типы ведения заметок.

Kirish

Qadimgi davrlarda axborotni saqlab qolish va uni keyingi avlodlarga yetkazish ehtiyoji yozuvning paydo bo'lishiga olib kelgan. O'sha davrda yozuv uchun materiallar kam bo'lganligi sababli, odamlar faqat eng muhim, voqeaning asosiy mazmunini aks ettira oladigan ma'lumotlarni yozishga harakat qilishgan. Kim (2019) ta'kidlaganidek: "Eslatma olish tarixi, ehtimol, ta'lim tarixidek qadimiydir. Chunki dastlabki o'qituvchilar davridayoq o'quvchilar ulardan eshitgan dars yoki ko'rsatmalarni yozib olishgan, ayniqsa yozuv tizimi yaratilganidan so'ng." (25-bet). Hozirgi kunda esa kerakli axborotni yozib olish va uni uzoq muddatga saqlash jarayoni "eslatma olish" deb ataladi. O'quv jarayonida deyarli har bir talaba biror bosqichda eslatma olishga majbur bo'lgan. O'qituvchilar bunga doimiy ravishda undaydilar, hatto ba'zan majburlaydilar. "Eslatma olish oliy ta'lim muassasalarida uzoq yillik akademik o'qitish an'alarining muhim qismini tashkil etadi va aynan shu ko'nikma talabalarning yuqori ta'limga xos belgilaridan biri hisoblanadi" (Siegel, 2022). Uning sodda va qulayligi sababli, eslatma olish faqat ta'lim sohasidagina emas, balki biznes, marketing va davlat boshqaruvi sohalarida ham keng qo'llanilmoqda. Ushbu adabiyot sharhi eslatma olish tushunchasi va uning ahamiyatini yoritadi. Shu bilan birga, sohada yetakchi hisoblangan olimlar olib borgan tadqiqot natijalarini ham ko'rsatib o'tadi. Ma'lumki, eslatma olish asosan ikki jarayonda – tinglash va o'qish vaqtida yuz beradi. Shuning uchun, bu ish eslatma olishning har ikkala shaklini – tinglash va o'qishdagi usullarini tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarning eslatma olish bo'yicha ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun tadqiqot asosida ba'zi usullar ham tavsiya etiladi.

Akademik muhitda eslatma olishning ahamiyati

Universitetda o'qiyotgan har bir talaba egallashi kerak bo'lgan eng muhim ko'nikmalardan biri bu – eslatma olishdir. Talabalar semestr davomida o'nlab ma'ruzalar va dars mashg'ulotlarida qatnashadilar. Ushbu bilimlarni puxta o'zlashtirish va saqlab qolish uchun ular qisqa va ravshan tarzda yozib olishlari zarur. Shu sababli, ko'plab olimlar tomonidan isbotlanganidek, eslatma olish mukammal o'quv usuli sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ipek (2018) eslatma olishni juda oddiy qilib quyidagicha ta'riflaydi: "Eslatma olish bu – keyinchalik murojaat qilish va eslab qolish uchun ma'lumotni hujjatlashtirish usulidir" (206-bet). Xuddi shunday, Özçakmak (2019) ham eslatma olishni kelajakda qo'llash uchun ramzlar yordamida qisqa, lekin muhim ma'lumotlarni yozib olish va tashqi xotira yaratish shakli sifatida ta'riflaydi.

Odamlar eslatma olish orqali ma'lumotni unutmazlik va kerakli vaqtda undan foydalanish imkoniyatini saqlab qoladilar. Biroq eslatma olish faqat ta'lim sohasidagina emas, balki kundalik hayotda ham qo'llaniladi. Masalan, do'stning

telefon raqamini yozib qo‘yish, do‘kon ro‘yxatini tuzish yoki mijozlar nomi va manzillarini yozish ham eslatma olish turidir. Ammo aynan akademik kontekstdagi eslatma olish – xususan ma’ruza tinglayotganda yoki maqola o‘qiyotganda – ancha murakkabroq bo‘lishi mumkin. Masalan, Piolat, Olive va Kellog (2019) fikricha: “Eslatmalar – bu darsni tinglash, o‘rganish yoki kuzatish jarayonida muallif tomonidan yozib olingan original kontentning qisqa mazmuni bo‘lib, u dars, kitob yoki boshqa eslab qolish zarur bo‘lgan vaziyatlarda ma’lumotni jamlash va saqlash uchun xizmat qiladi.”

Bu esa eslatma olish ko‘p bosqichli va murakkab jarayon ekanini anglatadi. Talaba bir vaqtning o‘zida professorni tinglashi, kerakli so‘zlarni tanlab yozib olishi, hamda bu eslatmalarni tartibli va mazmunli tarzda tashkil qilishi lozim. Shuningdek, Zuckerman (2019) ta’kidlaydi: “Eslatma olish talabadan ko‘p miqdordagi aqliy harakatni talab qiladi va natijada eslatmalar chalkash va tushunarsiz bo‘lib qolishi mumkin.” Demak, eslatma olish oddiy ma’lumot saqlash ko‘rinishidan akademik kontekstdagi murakkab strategiyaga aylanadi.

Eslatma olish ko‘p bosqichli va murakkab jarayon bo‘lishiga qaramay, uning foydalari juda katta. Axborot asrida yashayotganligimiz sababli, odamlar ko‘p sonli ma’lumotlar ichidan eng kerakli va asosiylarini ajratib olishlari zarur. Shuning uchun, eslatma olish akademik muhitda yanada muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Kobayashi (2006) ta’kidlaganidek: “Eslatma olish tushunishni yaxshilashda eng muhim vositalardan biridir.” Evans va Shively (2019) bu fikrni qo‘llab-quvvatlab, “Yaxshi eslatma olish ko‘nikmalari talabani hayotini ancha osonlashtiradi, chunki bu nafaqat kichik detallarni, balki umumiy mazmuni ham tushunishga yordam beradi”, deb yozadilar. Bundan tashqari, eslatmalar orqali ma’lumotlar miyada tizimli tarzda joylashadi va eslab qolish osonlashadi. Tsai, Wu, Crawford va Siegel (2018) olib borgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatdiki: “Eslatma olish bo‘yicha o‘quv mashg‘ulotlari talabalar tomonidan qabul qilinadigan ma’lumot miqdorini sezilarli darajada oshirgan.” Shunday qilib, samarali eslatma olish ma’ruzalarni yaxshi tushunishga imkon yaratadi va talabalar bunday mashg‘ulotlardan ijobiy taassurot bildirganlar.

Eslatma olishning turli turlari, ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari

Yozuv ilk bor paydo bo‘lgan davrlardan boshlab, odamlar uni yanada samarali va qulay qilish yo‘llarini ishlab chiqq boshladilar. Boshida bitta gil taxtachaga bitilgan sodda so‘zlar guruhidan boshlangan bu jarayon hozirda murakkab va mazmunli axborotni ifodalovchi tuzilmalarga aylandi. Eslatma olishning eng keng tarqalgan shakllaridan biri bu — an’anaviy eslatma olish usulidir. Bu usul juda sodda va deyarli har kim uchun mavjud, chunki faqat qog‘oz va ruchka kifoya qiladi. Soddaligiga qaramay, bu usul tinglash va o‘qish jarayonlarida juda samarali xizmat qiladi.

Mueller va Oppenheimer (2016) tomonidan o‘tkazilgan tadqiqotga ko‘ra, har qanday formatda qog‘ozga eslatma olgan talabalar, kompyuterda eslatma olgan

tengdoshlariga qaraganda faktlar va tushunchalar bo'yicha testlarda ancha yuqori natijalar ko'rsatgan. Boshqa tomondan, Evan va Shively (2019) shuni ta'kidlaydiki: "Odatdagi eslatma olish ko'nikmalaridan foydalangan talabalar, hatto akademik jihatdan yuqori natijaga ega bo'lganlar ham, dars davomida berilgan ma'lumotlarning 45% dan kamrog'ini yozib olganlar." Bundan tashqari, Kiewra (1995) qog'ozda eslatma olishning afzalliklarini qo'llab-quvvatlab: "Qog'ozga yozilgan eslatmalar o'rta maktab va nogiron talabalar uchun ayniqsa foydalidir", deb hisoblaydi.

Texnologiya rivojlanishi bilan eslatma olishning yangi shakli — raqamli eslatma olish paydo bo'ldi. Özçakmak (2019) bu haqda shunday deydi: "Texnologik imkoniyatlar talabalar uchun ko'plab qulayliklarni yaratdi va yozish uchun ketadigan vaqtni qisqartirdi" (582-bet). Raqamli eslatma olish Horney va Anderson-Inman (2009) tomonidan quyidagicha ta'riflanadi: "Bu eslatma olish usuli matn ichida yozuvlar qoldirish, izohlar qo'shish yoki topshiriqlarni bajarish uchun keyinroq foydalanish imkonini beruvchi vositalarni o'z ichiga oladi" (154-bet).

Garchi bu eng qulay va keng tarqalgan usullardan biri bo'lsa-da, uning ham ba'zi kamchiliklari mavjud. Masalan, Horney va boshqalar (2009) qo'lda yozilgan eslatmalar raqamli eslatmalarga qaraganda samaraliroq ekanini ta'kidlab, buni quyidagicha asoslashadi: qo'lda yozilgan eslatmalar chuqurroq tushunish, yaxshiroq eslab qolish va chalg'ituvchilarga kamroq berilish kabi ustunliklarga ega. Raqamli eslatmalar esa matnni tahrirlash, qidiruv, xavfsiz saqlash va ulashish imkoniyati bilan ajralib turadi (Ozuru va boshq., 2004). Umuman olganda, kompyuterlar talabalar uchun yozishdan ko'ra terish orqali ko'proq eslatmalar olish imkoniyatini yaratdi va qalam hamda qog'oz o'rnini klaviatura egalladi (Evans & Shively, 2019). Bugungi kunda talabalar dars paytida doskadagi yozuvlarni telefon orqali suratga olib, eslatma sifatida saqlab qo'yadilar (Özçakmak & Sarigöz, 2019). Bu esa texnologiya rivojlanishiga qaramasdan, eslatma olish an'anasining dolzarbligini saqlab qolayotganini ko'rsatadi.

Tinglash jarayonida eslatma olish usullari

Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, eslatma olishning asosiy sohalaridan biri bu — tinglab eslatma olishdir. Agar talabalar tinglangan darsdagi asosiy g'oyalarni yozib olmasalar, bir necha hafta o'tgach ularni eslashlari qiyinlashadi. Shu sababli, ko'pgina o'qituvchilar talabalarni eslatma olishga undaydilar, ba'zida esa bu jarayon majburiy ham bo'ladi.

Özçakmak (2019) olib borgan tadqiqotga ko'ra, talabalar orasida 61% eslatma olishni "tinglash asosida eslatma olish" deb bilsa, 31% esa "o'qish asosida eslatma olish" deb ta'kidlaydi (582-bet). Tinglash jarayonida keng qo'llaniladigan eslatma olish usullari quyidagilar: Gap usuli (Sentence Method), Aql xaritasi usuli (Mind Mapping), Rasmiy kontur tuzish (Formal Outline Procedure), Klasterlash (Clustering) va Kornel usuli (Cornel Method) (Hayati & Jalilifar, 2009).

Ular orasida eng mashhuri — Kornel usuli bo‘lib, bunda varaq uch bo‘lakka bo‘linadi: chap tomonda vertikal chiziq, pastda gorizontaal chiziq, markazda esa asosiy yozuvlar uchun keng maydon bo‘ladi. Pauk (2019) bu usulni “tabiiy o‘rganish sikli” deb ataydi, chunki u eslatma yozish, qayta ko‘rib chiqish va tushunishni baholash kabi bosqichlarni bitta hujjatda birlashtiradi (10-bet). Chambers va Northedge (2019) esa Kornel usulini “ma‘ruza vaqtida talabadan diqqatni jamlab, dalillarni tahlil qilishni talab qiladigan samarali strategiya” deb baholaydilar.

Biroq bu usul ilg‘or tinglash ko‘nikmasiga ega bo‘lgan talabalar uchun foydalidir. Siegel (2019) ta’kidlaganidek: “Eslatma olishning keyingi bosqichiga o‘tishdan oldin, samarali tinglashni ta’minlash shart” (215-bet). Shunday ekan, yaxshi eslatma olish samarali tinglashdan boshlanadi (Al-Musalli, 2015). Yuqorida tilga olingan usullardan foydalanish uchun talaba tinglayotgan matnni tez va aniq tushunishi kerak. Chunki dars paytida talaba hamma so‘zlarni emas, balki faqat asosiy kalit so‘zlarni yozib olishga e’tibor qaratadi (Kilickaya & Cokal-Karadas, 2009).

O‘qish jarayonida eslatma olish usullari

Yuqorida eslatib o‘tganimizdek, o‘qish asosida eslatma olish tinglash asosidagiga qaraganda kamroq tarqalgan. Bunga asosiy sabablardan biri — o‘qiyotgan matn allaqachon talabada mavjud bo‘lganligi, va u muhim joylarni chizib qo‘yishi, belgilashi yoki aylanma shaklda ajratib ko‘rsatishi mumkinligidadir. Shuning uchun, alohida hujjatda eslatma olish ehtiyoji kamayadi. Bu esa o‘qish jarayonida eslatma olishni tinglashga qaraganda ancha osonlashtiradi.

Wright va Wall (2015) ikkita tushunchani farqlaydi: “eslatma olish” (note-taking) va “eslatma yaratish” (note-making). Ularning izohlashicha, “eslatma olish” tinglash jarayoniga tegishli bo‘lsa, “eslatma yaratish” — o‘qish bilan bog‘liq. Ular ta’kidlaydiki, “eslatma yaratish” “eslatma olish”ga qaraganda ancha zavqli va erkinroq kechadi, chunki bu holatda o‘quvchi matnni o‘z xohishiga ko‘ra, shoshilmasdan tahlil qiladi. Ipek (2018) esa eslatma olishni til o‘rganishdagi eng oson ko‘nikmalardan biri deb hisoblaydi, garchi tinglashda talabadan nutq tezligiga moslashish talab qilinsa ham.

O‘qish jarayonida eslatma olishda keng qo‘llaniladigan usullardan biri — “Andazalash usuli” (Patterning method). Bu usulda o‘quvchi vizual elementlardan (rasmlar, shakllar) foydalanib asosiy ma’lumotlarni aniqlaydi va eslab qoladi. Smolkowski (2018) bu usulni “vizual o‘rganishga moyil bo‘lganlar uchun mos” deb hisoblaydi. Özçakmak (2019) esa bu usulni “ko‘p sezgi orqali o‘rganish imkonini beruvchi kinestetik o‘rganuvchilar uchun ham samarali” deb ta’riflaydi. Kesselman (2003) esa quyidagicha fikr bildiradi: “Inson miyasi eshitgan yoki o‘qigan ma’lumotni ma’lum bir andazaga solib olganida uni yaxshi eslab qoladi” (24-bet). Yulduzcha, doira, kvadrat yoki boshqa vizual shakllarni chizish eslatma olishda samaradorlikni oshiradi.

Shuningdek, keng tarqalgan usullardan yana biri — konturli shaklda eslatma olish (Outline form). Bu usul ko'p sonli eslatmalarni tartibli va mantiqiy ketma-ketlikda yozib borish imkonini beradi. Siegel (2022) ta'kidlaydi: "Talabalar eslatma olayotganda, ular har xil formatlardan (kontur, andaza, aql xaritasi va boshqalar) birini tanlab, kerakli ma'lumotlarni butunlay yoki qisqartma, parafraz shaklida yozib olishlari mumkin." Har bir o'quvchining uslubi har xil bo'lganligi sababli, mos usulni tanlashda shaxsiy did va malaka muhim ahamiyatga ega. Dunkel (2019) fikriga ko'ra, "Birinci va ikkinchi tilida mohir eslatma oluvchilar ma'lumotni qisqartma va ramzlar yordamida mantiqiy tuzilmalarga solib ifodalay oladilar" (207-bet).

Eslatma olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha maslahatlar

Samarali eslatma olish o'quvchining o'zlashtirish qobiliyatini oshirishda muhim vositadir. Ipek (2019) ta'kidlaydi: "Eslatma olish, ayniqsa akademik muhitga yangi kirib kelgan talabalar uchun qiyin va foydasiz tuyulishi mumkin, shuning uchun bu ko'nikma o'quv dasturlariga kiritilishi zarur" (4-bet). Shunday ekan, eslatma olishni rivojlantirish uchun quyidagi muhim jihatlar e'tiborga olinishi kerak:

Eng avvalo, o'quvchi o'zi olgan axborotni tushuna olishi lozim, aks holda mazmunga ega eslatma yozib bo'lmaydi. Al-Musalli (2015) fikricha: "Tilni tushunish — g'oya hosil qilishning eng muhim va birinchi bosqichidir" (140-bet). Kesselman (2003) esa shunday deydi: "Eslatma yozish paytida yozilgan so'zlarning sonidan ko'ra, ularning sifatiga e'tibor berish muhimroq." Özçakmak (2019) ham shu fikrni tasdiqlab: "Matndan ushlab qolingan asosiy birliklar soni, yozilgan eslatmalar miqdoridan ahamiyatliroqdir" (587-bet). Shunday ekan, eslatmalarni ko'p yozish emas, balki sifatli yozish zarur.

Va nihoyat, o'quvchi o'z shaxsiy o'quv uslubiga mos kelmaydigan eslatma olish strategiyasidan foydalanmasligi kerak. Masalan, ba'zi talabalar o'qituvchi tavsiya qilgani uchun ma'lum bir usuldan foydalanadilar. Bui, Myerson va Jansen (2019) shunday xulosa chiqaradi: "Kognitiv jihatdan farqli bo'lgan talabalar turlicha eslatma olish usullarini tanlaydi va ulardan turlicha samaradorlikka erishadi" (3-bet).

METODOLOGIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotda mustaqil va bog'liq o'zgaruvchilar o'rtasidagi sabab-oqibat aloqalarini aniqlash uchun sababiy-qiyosiy (causal-comparative) tadqiqot yondashuvidan foydalanildi. Ushbu yondashuv orqali mavjud tafovutlar yoki tendensiyalarning sabablari chuqur o'rganiladi. Asosiy maqsad – vaziyatlarni tabiiy holatida taqqoslash orqali o'zgarishlarni aniqlashdir (Karasar, 2016). Tadqiqotchi mustaqil o'zgaruvchining bog'liq o'zgaruvchiga ta'sirini aniqlashga intiladi.

Tadqiqot ishtirokchilari

Tadqiqotda Toshkent shahridagi International School of Finance, Technology and Science oliy ta'lim muassasasining ingliz tili yo'nalishida tahsil olayotgan 68 nafar talabasi ishtirok etdi. Ulardan 43 foizi ayollar, qolgan 57 foizi erkaklar bo'lib, yoshi 17

dan 20 gacha edi. Talabalar A va B guruhlariga tasodifiy tarzda taqsimlandi. 1-jadvalda talabalarning jinsi va akademik ko'rsatkichlariga qarab taqsimoti ko'rsatilgan.

1-jadval. Tadqiqot ishtirokchilarining demografik ko'rsatkichlari

Guruhlar	Soni	Foizi
O'quvchilar (Readers)	17	25%
O'quvchi-eslatmachilar	17	25%
Tinglovchilar	17	25%
Tinglovchi-eslatmachilar	17	25%
Jami	68	100%

Ma'lumotlarni yig'ish

Joylashtirish testi

Talabalarning o'qish va tinglab tushunish bo'yicha boshlang'ich darajasini aniqlash uchun joylashtirish testi qo'llanildi. Hutchinson va Waters (1987, Tsou & Chen, 2014) fikricha, joylashtirish testlari talabalarni akademik darajaga qarab tasniflash imkonini beradi. Davies & West (1989) esa bu testlar orqali talabalarning haqiqiy bilim darajasini baholash mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi.

Test 18 ta savoldan iborat bo'lib, 8 tasi to'g'ri-noto'g'ri savollar, 10 tasi esa ochiq javobli savollardan iborat edi. Ochiq savollar maksimal 80 ball (10 x 8), to'g'ri-noto'g'ri savollar esa 20 ball (8 x 2.5) baholandi. Umumiy maksimal ball – 100.

Ishonchlilik va haqiqiylik

Testning ishonchliligi va haqiqiyliги – natijalar aniqligi va doimiyliги bilan belgilanadi (Alderson va boshq., 1995). Henning (1987, Alderson, 1995 orqali) fikricha, test maqsadli ko'rsatkichlarni baholay olsa, u haqiqiy hisoblanadi. Shu sababli test matni 560 so'zli, 6 paragraflik, o'rta darajadagi ilmiy matn sifatida www.twee.com platformasida yaratilgan. "Iqlim o'zgarishi – tafakkur o'zgarishi" mavzusi asosida tuzilgan test eslatma olish va tushunish ko'nikmalarini baholashga mos keladi.

Jarayon

Talabalarni tanlash

Dastlab 92 nafar talaba orasidan 68 nafar ixtiyoriy asosda ishtirok etdi. A va B sinflar asosida guruhlar tashkil etildi: A sinfdagi talabalar o'qish, B sinfdagilar esa tinglash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun tanlandi. Har bir sinf 34 nafardan iborat bo'lib, ular yana 2 guruhga bo'lindi (O'quvchi/O'quvchi-eslatmachi, Tinglovchi/Tinglovchi-eslatmachi).

Amalga oshirish

O'quvchilar (A sinf) "Changing Climate, Changing Minds" matnini o'qishdi. O'quvchilardan eslatma olmaslik, eslatmachi-o'quvchilardan esa yozib borish talab qilindi. Mashg'ulot 50 daqiqa davom etdi.

Tinglovchilar (B sinf) matnni audio shaklida tinglashdi. Tinglovchilardan eslatma olmaslik, tinglovchi-eslatmachilardan esa yozib borish so'raldi. Ular ham 50 daqiqa davomida faoliyat olib borishdi.

Natijalar

3-jadval. Guruhlarning joylashtirish testidagi o'rtacha ballari

Guruhlar	N	O'rtacha ball	Standart og'ish
O'quvchilar	17	77.24	20.01
O'quvchi-eslatmachilar	17	87.02	12.63
Tinglovchilar	17	84.86	14.00
Tinglovchi-eslatmachilar	17	105.37	12.55
Jami	68	89.01	18.04

Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, eng yuqori ballni tinglab eslatma olgan talabalar (105.37) to'plashdi. Eng past ball esa faqat o'qigan talabalar tomonidan olindi (77.24).

4-jadval. O'rtacha GPA va test ballari

Ko'rsatkich	O'rtacha qiymat	Standart og'ish	N
Joylashtirish testi	89.01	18.04	68
Akademik GPA (4 lik)	3.38	0.53	68

5-jadval. Jinsiy farqlarga ko'ra ballar taqsimoti

Jins	N	O'rtacha ball
Ayollar	43	69.29
Erkaklar	25	58.70

T-test natijalariga ko'ra, statistik jihatdan ayollar va erkaklar o'rtasida sezilarli tafovut yo'q ($p > 0.05$).

Munozara

Ushbu tadqiqot eslatma olishning ikki asosiy komponentini tahlil qildi: tinglash asosida va o'qish asosida eslatma olish. Avvalgi ko'plab tadqiqotlar (Hayati & Jalilifar, 2009; İpek, 2018; Gourley, 2021) har bir komponentni alohida o'rgangan, ammo ularning samaradorligini taqqoslagan izlanishlar kam bo'lgan. Ushbu tadqiqot esa aynan shuni qamrab olgani bilan ahamiyatlidir.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, faqat o'qigan va eslatma yozganlar o'rtasida sezilarli tafovut yo'q. Biroq tinglab eslatma olganlar ancha yuqori natijalarga erishgan. Bu eslatma olish va tinglash birgalikda amalga oshirilganda ko'proq foyda berishini ko'rsatadi.

Akademik GPA va test ballari o'rtasidagi ijobiy bog'liqlik ham ko'rsatdi: yuqori GPAGA ega talabalar yuqori ball to'plashdi. Bu Daly (1983), Luo et al. (2016), Kiewra & Benton (1988) tadqiqotlari bilan mos keladi. Shu bilan birga, past GPAGA

ega talabalar ham eslatma olish bo'yicha o'rgatilsa, yaxshilanishi mumkinligi qayd etiladi.

Xulosa

Ushbu tadqiqot faqatgina ma'lumot beruvchi (informative) matn asosida olib borilgan bo'lib, uning natijalari boshqa turdagi matnlarga umumlashtirib bo'lmaydi. Kelgusida hikoya yoki bahsli matnlar asosida ham shunga o'xshash tadqiqotlar o'tkazish mumkin. Shuningdek, o'rta maktab, boshlang'ich maktab yoki boshqa yoshdagi guruhlar bilan ham o'rganish tavsiya etiladi. Chet tilini o'qitishda ham tinglash/o'qish asosida eslatma olishning ta'siri chuqurroq o'rganilishi mumkin.

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IKKI TILLI TALABALARNING AMALIY EHTIYOJLARI

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Abstrakt: Maqolada ta'kidlanishicha, kursning tuzilishidan tashqari, ushbu tashabbus zamonaviy qishloq xo'jaligining tobora o'sib borayotgan o'zaro bog'liqligini kengroq e'tirof etishni aks ettiradi. Agronomlarning ingliz tilida ishonchli va samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyati endi ikkinchi darajali mahorat emas, balki asosiy kompetensiyaga aylanmoqda. Shunday qilib, ushbu ESP (maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili) kursi mahalliy tajribani global yutuqlar bilan bog'laydigan ko'priklar vazifasini o'taydi. O'quv dasturining ehtiyojlarga asoslangan ta'limga urg'u berishi nazariy tushunchalarni tushunibgina qolmay, balki xalqaro muloqotlarda faol ishtirok etishga, shartnomalar bo'yicha muzokaralar olib borishga va muhim tadqiqot natijalari bilan almashishga talabalarni tayyorlashga qaratilgan amaliy qo'llashga intilishni ko'rsatadi. Madaniyatlararo hamshiralik modeli qo'llanilishi yana bir bor nozik muloqotning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi, bu butun dunyo bo'ylab qishloq xo'jaligi amaliyoti va savdo aloqalarini shakllantiradigan turli madaniy kontekstlarni tan oladi. Oxir oqibat, kursning maqsadi kelajakdagi agronomlarni global miqyosda barqaror va innovatsion qishloq xo'jaligi usullari bo'yicha samarali elchilarga aylantirish, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilishga o'z hissasini qo'shishdan iboratdir.

Kalit so'zlari: Qishloq xo'jaligi, ekologiya yo'nalishidagi til ko'nikmalari, madaniyatlararo sog'liqni saqlash, olim-agronomlar, shartnomalar va bosqichma-bosqich yo'riqnomalar, qishloq xo'jaligi bosma nashrlari.

Аннотация: В статье указывается, что инициатива двуязычия отражает более широкое признание растущей взаимосвязанности современного сельского хозяйства с другими странами. Способность агрономов уверенно и эффективно общаться на английском языке больше не является второстепенным навыком, а становится ключевой компетенцией. Таким образом, этот курс ESP (английский язык для специальных целей) действует как мост, соединяющий местный опыт с глобальными достижениями. Акцент учебной программы на обучении, основанном на потребностях, свидетельствует о стремлении к практическому применению, подготавливая студентов не только к пониманию теоретических концепций, но и к активному участию в международных диалогах, ведению переговоров по контрактам и обмену важными результатами исследований. Применение модели межкультурного ухода за культурами еще раз подчеркивает важность общения, признавая разнообразие контекстов, которые формируют сельскохозяйственные практики и торговые отношения во всем мире. В конечном счете, цель курса - расширить возможности будущих агрономов, чтобы они стали эффективными посланцами устойчивых и инновационных методов ведения сельского хозяйства

в глобальном масштабе, внося свой вклад в продовольственную безопасность и охрану окружающей среды.

Ключевые слова: Сельское хозяйство, языковые навыки, область экологии, межкультурное здравоохранение, ученые-агрономы, контракты и пошаговые инструкции, сельскохозяйственные печатные издания.

Abstract: The article indicates the results beyond the course's structure, the initiative reflects a broader recognition of the increasingly interconnected nature of modern agriculture. The ability of agronomists to engage confidently and effectively in English is no longer a peripheral skill, but a central competency. This ESP course (English for particular purposes), therefore, acts as a bridge, connecting local expertise with global advancements. The curriculum's emphasis on needs-based learning suggests a commitment to practical application, preparing students not just to understand theoretical concepts, but to actively participate in international dialogues, negotiate contracts, and share vital research findings. The adoption of the cross-cultural nursing model further underscores the importance of nuanced communication, acknowledging the diverse cultural contexts that shape agricultural practices and trade relationships worldwide. Ultimately, the course aims to empower future agronomists to become effective ambassadors for sustainable and innovative agricultural practices on a global scale, contributing to food security and environmental stewardship.

Kew words: Farming, Ecology-focused Language Skills, Intercultural Healthcare, Crop Scientists, Contracts & Step-by-Step Procedures, Farm-related Printed Works.

Введение. Выбранным контекстом ESP (английский для специальных целей) является английский язык в области экологии, преподавание которого ведется в государственном аграрном университете. Студенты, изучающие английский язык, – это будущие агрономы, работающие с управлением почвами и развитием сельскохозяйственных культур, а также с методами культивирования и использованием растений. Студенты находятся на допрофессиональном уровне, где основное внимание уделяется их обучению технологиям и необходимым продуктам, которые могут способствовать росту растений. В группе не более 17 студентов в возрасте от 20 до 25 лет. В группе смешанный гендерный состав, включающий 9 юношей и 8 девушек. Поскольку они студенты второго курса, они еще не имеют достаточного опыта в своей области. Они больше сосредоточены на научных знаниях, чем на практической части, но в конце семестра у них есть двухмесячная практика. Это дает им возможность применить научные знания на практике. Что касается их языковой подготовки, то аграрный университет не требует каких-либо предварительных знаний английского языка при поступлении. Однако студенты, которых я учу английскому, имеют базовый уровень английского языка, а именно, все являются учащимися среднего уровня. Поэтому обучать их английскому языку для их целей не представлялось сложным. Большинство девушек получили предварительные знания английского языка, когда учились в школе, а остальные, в основном юноши, имеют уровень B1 в образовательных центрах. Поскольку у них разный языковой опыт, они потратили разное количество времени на

достижение этого уровня. Девушки начали изучать язык в возрасте 14 лет, когда учились в 8 классе школы, а те (юноши), у которых есть сертификат B1 CEFR, посвятили год изучению языка с нуля в различных образовательных центрах Ташкента, таких как Cambridge, Internation и т. д. Поскольку они будущие агрономы, они должны хорошо говорить, чтобы общаться с иностранными инвесторами с целью предоставления технологий или необходимых органических продуктов для почвы или растений, а также обладать навыками письма и чтения для работы с документами при импорте и экспорте выращенных фруктов и овощей в другие зарубежные страны. Таким образом, курс ESP направлен на предоставление агрономам языковых инструментов для изучения терминологии или соглашений и инструкций, касающихся их профессиональной сферы. И последнее, но не менее важное: курс совершенствует и тренирует навыки учащихся на основе анализа потребностей их области посредством ролевых игр или описательных заданий в течение года. В частности, использованный метод анкетирования, приведенный ниже, продемонстрировал их слабые и сильные стороны в языке, что помогло мне организовать учебные материалы и разработать задания, относящиеся к сельскому хозяйству.

Обзор литературы: Первый выбранный мной курс - "Английский для межкультурного ухода за больными" Сьюзен Бошер. Этот выбор обусловлен тем, что курс направлен на развитие всех аспектов английского языка у студентов, таких как устное общение с пациентами, навыки аудирования и конспектирования, а также навыки письма и чтения, и все это с использованием интерактивных методологических подходов. Кроме того, курс ориентирован на материалы, основанные на контексте, такие как учебники по сестринскому делу или статьи из журналов, когда студенты обучаются языку. В настоящее время сельское хозяйство - это глобальная индустрия, объединяющая людей из разных стран в одной области. Выбранный курс позволяет обучать конкретной лексике и техническому языку, используемым в сельском хозяйстве, таким как различное понимание сельскохозяйственного опыта и практики, а также различное восприятие продуктов питания/продуктов. Особенно для навыков говорения и аудирования он улучшает взаимодействие с фермерами, сельскими общинами или международными сельскохозяйственными партнерами. Курс ESP требует от преподавателя больше исследований при разработке и планировании контекста конкретной области.

Второй выбранный курс - "Письмо с использованием корпусов в конкретной области" Мэгги Чарльз - предназначен для аспирантов, имеющих продвинутый уровень, например, 7/7,5 по IELTS или 100/110 по TOEFL. Основная причина, по которой я считаю этот курс полезным для моих студентов, заключается в том, что его структура полезна для моих студентов бакалавриата

с точки зрения письма с помощью корпусов. Во-первых, я должна упомянуть о важности коммуникации для исследований и маркетинга сельскохозяйственной продукции. Например, студенты пишут исследовательскую работу, и она должна быть четкой и убедительной, чтобы быть опубликованной или отправленной в какие-либо компании. Во-вторых, маркетинг сельскохозяйственной продукции требует привлекательного языка для привлечения потребителей. В-третьих, корпуса используются в сельскохозяйственной коммуникации путем выявления тенденций в сельскохозяйственной лексике и полутерминологии. С точки зрения практической части выбранного курса "Письмо с использованием корпусов в конкретной области" Мэгги Чарльз, студенты могут анализировать сельскохозяйственные публикации в своей области и будут осведомлены о текущих проблемах и решениях в мире сельского хозяйства посредством письменных отчетов или статей. Хотя продолжительность курса составляет 6 недель, он учит писать по конкретным областям. Кроме того, курс учит использовать современные технологии при проверке письменных работ с помощью корпусов, и это повышает способность учителя использовать инструменты. «Выбранное программное обеспечение предоставляет несколько инструментов с различными возможностями для изучения языка» (Anthony 2014a; 2014b). Оба курса могут способствовать разработке моей дальнейшей программы ESP.

Практическая часть анализа потребностей: Важно заранее определить текущий уровень языка студентов перед началом курса ESP, и поэтому множественные методы в качестве количественной помощи помогают собрать субъективную информацию о студентах. Существуют различные способы количественного метода, такие как опросы, интервью или просто устный опросник. Как преподаватель ESP, предпочтительно проводить интервью и тесты с вопросами, подготовленными заранее. Интервью - это не только самый ценный инструмент, но и доступный и индивидуальный метод проверки с точки зрения их желаний, базовых знаний, сильных и слабых сторон или даже стиля обучения от преподавателя ESP. «Начиная с анализа потребностей: по крайней мере, практикующий ESP дополнит анализ потребностей кратким обзором своих собственных, сосредоточив внимание на областях, которые, по его мнению, необходимо включить в программу курса» (Menkabu & Harwood, 2014; Grammatosi & Harwood, 2014). В аграрном университете, расположенном в Ташкенте, где я проводил анализ потребностей, обучаются студенты, специализирующиеся в области агрономии, которая включает изучение почвы, растений, насекомых, овощей и фруктов. Группа состояла из 8 девушек и 4 юношей, всего 12 студентов. Все студенты демонстрируют средний уровень владения английским языком. Согласно результатам анкетирования, более 61%

набрали 6-6,5 баллов, 30% – 7 баллов по системе IELTS, а остальные соответствуют уровню C1 (CEFR). Поскольку моими целевыми студентами являются учащиеся университета, у них ограничены возможности для трудоустройства и получения практического опыта в своей сфере. Хорошие коммуникативные навыки при взаимодействии с иностранными инвесторами и навыки понимания специализированных текстов при составлении международных соглашений/документов, а также умение понимать состав продукта, опираясь на инструкции, крайне важны для их будущей работы в сельском хозяйстве. В связи с этим, целью курса ESP является предоставление студентам достаточного объема знаний в области сельского хозяйства, включая изучение необходимой лексики и грамматических конструкций для повышения эффективности их коммуникации.

Основными участниками исследования являются студенты аграрного университета. Я работаю здесь преподавателем английского языка для курса ESP в течение 6 месяцев, и общий уровень владения английским языком у студентов – уверенный средний. Они активно участвуют в моих занятиях. Несмотря на довольно хорошее понимание языка в целом, они испытывают трудности с некоторыми терминами в плане лексики, что мешает им при общении, приводя к недопониманию, а также при чтении в специфическом сельскохозяйственном контексте. Иногда они просят говорящего повторить сказанное немного медленнее в середине разговора, чтобы лучше понять. Что касается языковой подготовки студентов, они изучали язык в школе и в нескольких образовательных центрах. Поскольку все мои студенты – узбеки, они общаются со своими родителями на родном языке. Как следствие, это ограничивает их возможности для широкой практики языка. Они жалуются на проблемы с пониманием текстов для чтения, связанных с сельскохозяйственными отчетами/книгами, а некоторые студенты говорят, что трудно бегло говорить с иностранцами, когда обсуждаются сельскохозяйственные темы. Кроме того, у них есть лабораторные эксперименты и поездки на поля, а также работа над проектами, где потребуется свободное владение английским языком, и выбранный курс ESP внесет эффективный вклад в создание и разработку моего курса.

В качестве **вторых заинтересованных** лиц я решил проанализировать выводы преподавателей, которые, как и я, ведут тот же предмет, об опыте преподавания и компетенции студентов. Я постарался охватить преподавателей ESP всех возрастов, так как все они могут иметь разные взгляды на одних и тех же студентов. Что касается опыта работы преподавателей, то 8 преподавателей, работающих там в качестве моих коллег, имеют не менее 4 лет опыта в этой области и не менее 5 месяцев работы с моими основными заинтересованными

лицами (моими студентами). Поскольку родным языком всех преподавателей является узбекский, это очень помогает мне понять проблемы узбекских студентов с языком для конкретной области, а также найти решения и способы улучшения их языковой подготовки. Интервью было выбрано в качестве метода сбора данных для обеих групп заинтересованных лиц, чтобы узнать об их проблемах и потребностях (слабых сторонах в языке). Как пояснил Вудроу (2018), предпочтения и выводы заинтересованных лиц о курсе ESP важны при анализе потребностей студентов перед началом всего курса.

Для сбора данных среди заинтересованных лиц использовался метод триангуляции. Во-первых, им было предложено написать краткое изложение, основанное на имеющихся знаниях о том, что они узнали из курса ESP к настоящему времени. Они должны были записать все, начиная с методов и материалов преподавателя и заканчивая системой оценки, и даже внести некоторые предложения по улучшению курса. Во-вторых, было проведено интервью по теме анализа потребностей. Оно предоставило преподавателю и практикам честные анонимные ответы, включающие 15 вопросов для студентов и 13 вопросов для преподавателей. Последним этапом стал онлайн-опросник, направленный на анализ навыков, требующих первоочередного развития, и трудностей, связанных с этими навыками.

Начиная с интервью, было выявлено множество аспектов, таких как их опасения, предпочтения и слабые стороны. Например, рассмотрим опасения студентов по поводу их текущего уровня:

Вопросы для интервью со студентами (первые заинтересованные лица):

1) Где вы начали изучать язык?

У меня было много учителей в школе, которые проводили интересные уроки, и я также посещал несколько образовательных центров. Я отдельно занимался грамматикой, потому что мне было сложно переводить предложения с одного языка на другой. У меня было много учебников по грамматике, и я пытался самостоятельно изучать ее, но не был уверен в правильности перевода предложений, и сейчас это ограничивает меня в выражении своих мыслей при переводе.

2) Что побудило вас изучать английский язык в связи с вашим интересом к сельскому хозяйству? Почему вы выбрали эту область для обучения?

Когда я был школьником, меня интересовало понимание английских фильмов и песен, и со временем английский стал необходимостью в учебе и в мире в целом. В настоящее время я побывал в нескольких странах благодаря возможностям развития сельского хозяйства. Я заметил, что английский

является доминирующим языком в моей сфере, так как он позволяет обмениваться знаниями, быть в курсе новостей, изменений и инноваций в сельском хозяйстве одновременно с молодежью, такой как мы, а также открывает лучшие возможности для работы.

3) Какой у вас сейчас уровень? 6-6,7

4) На каком языке вы говорите дома? Только на узбекском

5) С какими основными трудностями вы сталкиваетесь при изучении языка? (чтение, говорение, аудирование, письмо)

Когда у нас есть отчёты или соглашения с разными странами, бывает сложно понять каждое их условие при чтении, и мы вынуждены пользоваться переводчиком Google. Кроме того, нас часто приглашают на встречи с инвесторами из таких стран, как Китай и Индонезия, в качестве волонтеров-стикеров, и в такие моменты при разговоре проявляются слабые стороны — паузы и сомнения в речи. Это снижает самооценку.

6) В каком из навыков вы чувствуете себя более уверенно? Я могу сказать, что понимаю, когда слушаю выступающих или людей, говорящих на английском, а также умею писать предложения или электронные письма.

7) Какой тип ученика вы? Визуальный, аудиальный или кинестетический. Я предпочитаю практиковаться на уроке с использованием визуальных материалов, чтобы лучше представить и глубже понять тему.

8) Что вы находите трудным при чтении сельскохозяйственных статей или отчетов? Обычно сельскохозяйственные отчеты или соглашения содержат полутерминологию и техническую лексику, особенно когда объясняются компоненты продуктов, и это вызывает путаницу при понимании значений предложений.

9) Вам нравится работать в группе, с одноклассниками или индивидуально? Это зависит от вида деятельности, но кажется интересным и экономит время, когда нас делят на группы или пары. 10) *What makes you excited/amazed in Agricultural English? To communicate with people from other countries when they make agreements or contracts in terms of products that can be imported or exported. Especially, when they invite us suggestions or opportunities to go abroad and develop the career.*

11) На какие навыки следует уделять больше внимания в вашем сельскохозяйственном английском? На самом деле нам нужны все навыки одновременно, но если говорить о главных, то это чтение и говорение.

12) Какие у вас есть опасения относительно вашего текущего уровня? Хотя мой общий уровень английского достаточно хорош, чтобы понимать контексты, я не могу ответить, когда инвесторы просят меня объяснить компоненты продукта, особенно когда речь идет о терминологии.

Результаты: В результате было выявлено, что у студентов есть разные проблемы с языком. Например, большинство из них отметили слабые стороны в письменной и устной речи при производстве речи. Кроме того, некоторые подчеркивают трудности в понимании терминов, связанных с темой, в то время как другие учащиеся не могут ответить на вопросы во время разговора из-за недостаточного понимания терминов. (Изображения a/b/c/d ниже показывают статистику)

a)

Which of the language aspects are less confident about?

Копировать

12 ответов

b)

Which of the skill are you more confident about?

Копировать

12 ответов

c)

What part seems difficult on reading?

Копировать

12 ответов

d)

What part seems difficult on speaking?

Копировать

12 ответов

Findings

Результат: Диаграмма показывает, на каком уровне находятся студенты, а также процентное соотношение навыков, в которых они сильны и слабы.

Общий результат: Согласно статистике, говорение является для учащихся сложным навыком, так как они часто делают паузы и испытывают трудности с пониманием терминов. Письмо оказывается самым слабым навыком, что свидетельствует о значительных трудностях в структурировании идей и эффективном выражении мыслей.

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Needs assessment of a certain group of students

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda Yunusobod tumanidagi Agrarian litseyida ikki yildan beri ingliz tili o'qituvchisining 17 yoshdagi 15 nafar ikkinchi kurs talabalarining bilan faoliyati davomida til mahorati va o'rganish jarayoni o'rganiladi. Talabalar ingliz tilidagi mahorat darajalari turlicha bo'lib, ular orasida 3 nafar talabada boshlang'ich (elementar) daraja, 8 nafar talabada oldingi o'rta (pre-intermediate) daraja va 6 nafar talabada o'rta (intermediate) daraja mavjud. O'rta darajadagi talabalar 10 yoshdan boshlab ingliz tilini o'rganib, kuchli muloqot ko'nikmalariga va turli mavzularda insho va hikoyalar yozish qobiliyatiga ega, biroq rasmiy yozuvni yanada takomillashtirish uchun qo'shimcha mashq qilishlari zarur. Pre-intermediate darajadagi talabalar litseyda birinchi kursda ingliz tilini o'rganishni boshlagan bo'lib, savollarga tushunish va javob berish qobiliyatiga ega, ammo lug'at bazasi cheklanganligi sababli ba'zan to'xtab qolishadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til mahorati, Ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari, Agrarian litseyi, Ikkinchi kurs talabalar, Muloqot ko'nikmalari, Talaffuz muammolari, Ona tilining ta'siri (o'zbek tili), Farqlangan ta'lim, O'rganishda sabr-toqat, Fikr-mulohazalar va tuzatish, til egallash.

Abstract: This study examines the language proficiency and learning dynamics of a group of 15 second-year students, aged 17, at an Agrarian Lyceum in the Yunusabad region, where a teacher has been teaching English for two years. The students exhibit varying English proficiency levels: elementary (3 students), pre-intermediate (8 students), and intermediate (6 students). Intermediate learners, who have studied English since the age of ten, demonstrate strong communication skills and the ability to write essays and stories, though they require further practice to enhance formal writing. Pre-intermediate students, having started English in their first year at the lyceum, can understand and respond to questions but often hesitate due to limited vocabulary. Elementary students, new to English with only three months of study, can construct simple sentences using basic tenses. Pronunciation challenges persist across all levels, influenced by their native Uzbek language. Notably, students

display strong motivation and resilience, actively seeking feedback and striving to improve despite exam setbacks.

Key words: Language proficiency, English learners, Agrarian Lyceum, Second-year students, Communication skills, Pronunciation challenges, Native language influence (Uzbek), Differentiated instruction, Resilience in learning, Feedback and correction, Language acquisition.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается уровень владения языком и динамика обучения группы из 15 студентов второго курса, возрастом 17 лет, в Аграрном лицее в районе Юнусабад, где учитель преподает английский язык уже два года. Студенты демонстрируют разные уровни владения английским языком: элементарный (3 студента), предсредний (8 студентов) и средний (6 студентов). Студенты среднего уровня, изучающие английский с десяти лет, показывают хорошие коммуникативные навыки и способность писать эссе и рассказы, хотя им требуется дополнительная практика для улучшения формального письма. Студенты предсреднего уровня, начавшие изучать английский в первом курсе лицея, могут понимать и отвечать на вопросы, но часто колеблются из-за ограниченного словарного запаса. Студенты элементарного уровня, начинающие изучать английский всего три месяца назад, умеют строить простые предложения, используя основные времена.

Ключевые слова: владение языком, изучающие английский, Аграрный лицей, студенты второго курса, коммуникативные навыки, проблемы произношения, влияние родного языка (узбекский), дифференцированное обучение, стойкость в обучении, обратная связь и коррекция, овладение языком.

Background profiles of learners

Since teaching as an English teacher at Agrarian lyceum in Yunusabad region for 2 years, there are 15 students in my group whose ages are 17 years old. There are 1st and 2nd course students in the lyceum and my target learners are 2nd course pupils. Students' language levels are not the same, namely their levels are different, 3 of them are elementary level, 8 students are pre-intermediate and 6 students are intermediate level. Students whose levels are intermediate have been learning English since they are ten. The students can easily communicate with others in English and write any essays or stories on any topic. They just need more practice on writing in order to write essays as formal as possible. When it comes to pre-intermediate students, they learned it when they were 1st course at this lyceum by their interest. They are able to understand and even reply to the given questions but sometimes with pauses and hesitations because they do not have enough vocabulary base. The lowest level students are elementary ones who started English just 3 months ago. Making just simple sentences with several tenses such as Present Simple, Present Continuous or Future Simple is easy for them. Admittedly, in all three levels students still have pronunciation problems. As their L (1) is Uzbek, some words are challenging to pronounce especially if one letter (syllable or vowel is pronounced) differently. Although their level is not similar, their goal is the same which is to get IELTS 7+. The duration of the class is 80 minutes and there are 3 lessons in odd days of the week in a semester. Time is enough to divide them to 3 groups in terms of their levels and teach grammar and vocabulary for all levels. All in

all, they have huge interest and effort to learn the language because even if they fail on exams they do not give up and ask me to explain their mistakes and some time to correct them.

Needs Assessment

1) *What is the **first thing** you do when you are asked to teach a new course?* (Viana et al., 2019, p. 12).

Justification: There are several **things** to do when a teacher starts a new course such as level of the students, weak points or skills in a language as well as their needs from learning English (for business, for exam in the future studying process, marketing, engineering). My students want to learn it for their future career.

Answer: The initial part of the new course is identifying the **level** of my target learners and preparing materials in terms of their level. Because if knowledge and materials are not suitable to learners level, they just may lose their time instead of improving their English. Besides, their **weak point(s)** should be determined and analyzed the mistakes. They should be given/shown the ways how to decrease the numbers of mistakes and how to make the weak points into strong skills. Materials and teaching with different, interactive methods can be one of the most useful ways to become your English developed.

2) *How do students like to learn English?* (Viana et al., 2019, p. 14).

Justification: Whenever I am given a group of students who want to learn English, I am always interested in whether themselves like to learn the language or not. It is very important to have a desire for learning a language on themselves.

Answer: Unfortunately, I cannot say that all of my students learn English by their desire. Admittedly, English is already international language, some of my students study because they need it in the future, even if they do not like it. However, I have to be the kind of teacher that it is my responsibility to explain even through some examples, that English is actually an interesting language and that it opens the door to many opportunities. The rest of my students love to learn for English accent because of watching a lot of English movies especially when they communicate with native people they are motivated and run to learn it until they completely comprehend or reply in the speech. Therefore I bring them to the destinations where multiple tourists can be came across in order to feel real English accent.

3) *What goals do parents have for their children?* (Linse, 1993, p. 44).

Justification: As soon as children are born, they see their first teachers namely, their father and mother, and begin to receive knowledge from them. So, if we imagine a child as a high building, parents are the builders of that building, that is, they are the masters who lay the pillars/foundations.

Answer: A child learns behavior in society, how to communicate with people with respect and thirst for knowledge from his/her parents. If parents realize how great

and inexhaustible wealth science is and love it, teachers will not suffer from the incompetence or irresponsibility of the learners they are teaching. In addition, it is very important for parents to develop the child's self-control, cope with stressful situations and always be respectful for others' ideas and thoughts regardless of nationality and religion.

4) *What language(s) do students use when talking to their friends?* (Linse, 1993, p.40) *Justification:* Although my students L (1) is Uzbek, they mostly speak Russian, sometimes they mix 3 languages at a time by code switching. They get the code words and use them in their speech and it seems very clear to understand each other. *Answer:* I do not totally agree with the idea about when a person learns another language, he should completely use only the language he is learning in terms of listening, speaking or writing even there can be seen some mistakes on producing. Because comparing with L (1) or explaining something in mother tongue is a good way to learn any language. Especially, students can explain the task or ask the new words on their native language and it could easily help to learners to indicate the intake.

5) *What do your children need to know to get a good job?* (Linse, 1993, p. 46).

Justification: Nowadays children/teenagers dream about how to earn much money by different fields such as business, engineering or marketing without working on themselves, but few of them reality that knowledge is a foundation of everything.

Answer: It is a fact that the representatives of each field are required to know the English language first. No matter what field people work in, be it medicine or an architect, knowing English has become a mandatory condition. Children not only learn English, but also learn another field (designing, nursing, teaching) will provide them with a good job and income in the future.

6) *“What tasks are performed in English?”* (Viana et al., 2019, p. 14).

Justification: The question refers to determine students' level and age regardless of culture when the task is made/chosen.

Answer: It is connected with students' prior knowledge which he/she already learned, because the purpose of the task is to understand the difficult topic through practice. For example, if they are active in group working, tasks done with group are much more effective or peer working is also beneficial for those who do not prefer group working.

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ВЛАДЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКОМ — НЕОТЪЕМЛЕМАЯ ЧАСТЬ УСПЕШНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: В статье анализируется значимость изучения иностранных языков. Отмечается, что влияние процесса глобализации на современную культуру, взаимодействия людей в процессе межкультурной коммуникации, требует знания иностранного языка, который является важным аспектом образования успешных личностей. На данный момент владение иностранным языком является одним из ключевых факторов успешного образования и предоставляет конкурентное преимущество.

Ключевые слова: иностранные языки, глобализация, коммуникация, преподавание, образование.

Annotation: The article analyzes the importance of learning foreign languages. It highlights that the impact of globalization on modern culture and human interaction in the process of intercultural communication requires knowledge of a foreign language, which is a vital aspect of educating successful individuals. At present, proficiency in a foreign language is one of the key factors of effective education and provides a competitive advantage.

Keywords: foreign languages, globalization, communication, teaching, education.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada chet tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Globalizatsiya jarayonining zamonaviy madaniyatga ta'siri, madaniyatlararo muloqot jarayonida insonlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqalar chet tilini bilishni talab qiladi, bu esa muvaffaqiyatli shaxslarni tarbiyalashda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda chet tilini bilish samarali ta'limning asosiy omillaridan biri bo'lib, raqobatbardosh ustunlikni ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tillari, globallashuv, muloqot, o'qitish, ta'lim.

В современном мире ценность владения иностранными языками трудно переоценить. Взаимное общение и обмен информацией крайне важны для взаимопонимания между государствами в экономической, социальной и

культурной сфере. Взаимодействие и сотрудничество между странами напрямую зависят от умения людей понимать иностранные языки. Большинство людей осведомлены о преимуществах знания иностранных языков в профессиональной деятельности. Сегодня людям открываются многочисленные возможности за рубежом, и не только работа: знание иностранных языков является неременным условием для их реализации. Использование иностранного языка – также отличный способ познакомиться с народом и культурой его страны. Прекрасно и мотивирует осознание, что знание иностранного языка расширяет горизонты, где нашего родного языка недостаточно. Динамика современного мира диктует новые условия нашей повседневности. Стремительно развиваются коммуникационные технологии. Преподавание иностранных языков в школах всех уровней, его постоянное улучшение и прогресс неразрывно связаны с общим развитием. Жизнь требует от людей новых навыков общения и компетенций. Умение говорить на иностранном языке ценно не только в повседневной жизни, но и в профессиональной сфере. Необходимо начинать изучение иностранных языков с начальной школы и продолжать его системное изучение на протяжении всего периода школьного образования. Следовательно, преподаванием иностранных языков и его совершенствованием занимается и образовательная политика, которая определяет приоритеты, цели и содержание образования.

Преподавание иностранных языков постоянно меняется и корректируется, отвечая на вызовы современного общества. В истории образования иностранные языки и их преподавание всегда были ключевым аспектом как в общем, так и в профессиональном образовании. В современном мире мы наблюдаем глобализацию — формирование смешанной мировой культуры, переплетение национальных традиций, укрепление сотрудничества между странами. Этот процесс проявляется в унификации и объединении различных сторон жизни людей — их мироощущения и мировоззрения, политики и экономики, социальной жизни и производства, науки и образования, культуры и искусства, религии и языка, спорта и т. д. Процессы мировой глобализации и интеграции вызвали резкий рост межкультурных контактов во всех областях нашей жизни. В неё прочно вошли такие ситуации межкультурного общения, как обучение по обмену в школах и вузах, стажировки ученых, международные конференции, совместные предприятия, туристические поездки, выставки, гастролы, спортивные соревнования и так далее.

Таким образом, знание иностранных языков становится одним из ключей к успешной адаптации в социуме. С развитием международных деловых связей, освоением новых зарубежных технологий и расширением профессионального сотрудничества с иностранными специалистами выросла потребность в

специалистах, владеющих иностранными языками. Эти специалисты нужны все большему количеству компаний и учреждений, а существующий спрос на языки стимулирует открытие курсов иностранных языков, лингвистических центров и других учебных заведений, предлагающих услуги по обучению иностранным языкам.

В настоящее время английский язык как иностранный доминирует практически во всех областях жизни. Для большинства изучающих английский как иностранный, он важен для повышения уровня образования и расширения круга общения. Язык становится средством международного общения, только если его особая роль признается многими странами и народами. Английский язык признан официальным государственным языком во многих странах мира. Во многих странах (более 100), он становится приоритетным на всех ступенях образования, от дошкольных учреждений до аспирантуры. Английский язык в наши дни развивается по всем направлениям: родной, иностранный и официальный государственный язык. По этим причинам около 3 миллиардов человек используют английский как средство общения, и это беспрецедентное глобальное распространение языка. Однако статус международного языка зависит не от количества говорящих. Международный статус языка определяется не его лексическим богатством, красотой звучания, культурными традициями, литературными и музыкальными шедеврами, количеством носителей, а зависит от сильной централизованной власти, военной и экономической мощи, политической силы и перспектив сотрудничества. Вся история цивилизаций свидетельствует в пользу этого факта. Даже распространение английского языка связано с интенсивной и продолжительной колониальной политикой Великобритании, начиная со Средних веков и по сей день. Завоевания, подчинение и навязывание неродного языка покоренным народам — самый известный способ распространения любого языка. Авторитет международного языка завоевывается сильной экономикой, а не только военными походами. Более того, распространению английского способствовали не только экономические факторы, но и современные технологии, СМИ, Интернет и, в конечном итоге, глобализация культуры, мира и общения в целом. Стремление к прогрессу в науке и технике стало важным фактором для международного сотрудничества, и язык международного общения стал, как никогда актуален. Просвещение и образование стали краеугольным камнем успеха индивида в социуме.

Итак, английский язык стал в эпицентре международного внимания, в основном, из-за мощного экономического развития и процветания Великобритании. Преимущества использования языка международного общения очевидны. Однако существует мнение и опасность исчезновения языков из-за

засилья английского и пропаганды английских ценностей. Эти опасности трудно игнорировать. Изучая английский, заменяя им родной, мы вытесняем из своего сознания национальную модель поведения и мировосприятия, то есть становимся более уязвимыми к манипулированию. Трудно предположить, что превращение английского языка в универсальный и глобальный может продолжаться всегда, исходя из борьбы за мировое господство и лидерство других мировых держав, например, Китая, Кореи, России и других .

Следовательно, можно заключить, что изучение родного и иностранного языка полезно для каждого индивида, без замещения одного другим, и на определенном этапе психического развития личности. Те, кто, кроме родного языка, владеют еще хотя бы одним, производят более позитивное впечатление. В наше время, когда международный бизнес и работа за границей стали нормой, владение хотя бы одним иностранным языком практически необходимо для населения. Не исключено, что при приеме на работу знание хотя бы одного иностранного языка является требованием компаний.

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LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY

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Annotation: This article explores the evolution of language teaching methodology and pedagogy, focusing on modern didactic approaches and classroom innovations. The paper investigates methods that effectively foster linguistic competence, emphasizing communicative competence, task-based learning, and technology-integrated strategies. Drawing from recent academic literature and classroom-based research, this article highlights best practices that align with learner-centered education in 21st-century classrooms.

Keywords: language teaching methodology, pedagogy, linguistic competence, communicative language teaching, didactic innovation, classroom strategies, task-based learning

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola til o'qitish metodologiyasi va pedagogikasining evolyutsiyasini o'rganadi, zamonaviy didaktik yondashuvlar va sinfdagi innovatsiyalarga e'tibor qaratadi. Maqolada lingvistik kompetensiyani samarali rivojlantiruvchi metodlar, jumladan, kommunikativ kompetensiya, topshiriqqa asoslangan o'qitish va texnologiyalarga integratsiyalashgan strategiyalar tahlil qilinadi. So'nggi ilmiy adabiyotlar va amaliy tadqiqotlarga tayanilgan holda, maqola 21-asrda o'quvchi markazli ta'limga mos eng yaxshi tajribalarni ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'qitish metodologiyasi, pedagogika, lingvistik kompetensiya, kommunikativ til o'qitish, didaktik innovatsiya, sinf strategiyalari, topshiriqqa asoslangan o'qitish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается развитие методологии и педагогики преподавания языков с акцентом на современные дидактические подходы и инновации в классе. Исследуются методы, способствующие эффективному развитию лингвистической компетенции, с особым вниманием к коммуникативному обучению, обучению на основе задач и стратегиям с использованием технологий. Основываясь на современных научных источниках и исследованиях в классе, статья подчеркивает лучшие практики, соответствующие обучению, ориентированному на учащегося в условиях XXI века.

Ключевые слова: методология преподавания языка, педагогика, лингвистическая компетенция, коммуникативное обучение языку, дидактические инновации, стратегии в классе, обучение на основе заданий.

Traditional teaching methods that rely heavily on lecturing and rote memorization are no longer sufficient to meet the diverse needs of modern learners. Today's classrooms require dynamic, student-centered approaches that integrate real-life communication, collaborative tasks, interdisciplinary content, and technology. Didactics — the science of teaching — has evolved to prioritize interactive, meaningful learning experiences that promote linguistic competence and critical thinking. The modern classroom becomes a space where learners are not passive recipients but active participants.

One of the most widely used modern methodologies is Communicative Language Teaching, which focuses on the ability to communicate meaningfully in real-life situations. Unlike traditional grammar-heavy methods, CLT emphasizes speaking, listening, and interaction. For example, a CLT classroom may include pair-work activities such as role-plays, interviews, or “Find someone who...” games where students must use target vocabulary and grammar structures to achieve communicative goals. The aim is fluency and confidence, not perfection. Second one, Task-Based Learning is a method where students learn language through meaningful tasks that resemble real-world activities. Instead of studying language forms in isolation, learners complete tasks such as planning a trip, creating a menu, or solving a problem collaboratively. A key strength of TBL is its emphasis on functional language use, problem-solving, and collaboration. For instance, students may be asked to organize a class party, negotiate a budget, and present their plan to peers, thereby practicing relevant vocabulary and grammar in context. Next one, Project-Based Learning takes TBL a step further by involving long-term, in-depth projects that integrate multiple skills and subjects. Projects like creating a class magazine, producing a short film, or researching local history encourage students to take responsibility for their learning. PBL promotes autonomy, creativity, and deeper understanding, as students must gather information, make decisions, and reflect on their process. Teachers act as facilitators, guiding learners through each phase of the project. CLIL refers to teaching content subjects (such as geography, biology, or history) through a second language, usually English. This dual-focused method allows students to acquire both subject knowledge and language skills simultaneously. For example, a science lesson on “The Water Cycle” may include vocabulary like “evaporation,” “condensation,” and “precipitation” in English, supported by visuals and hands-on experiments. CLIL promotes contextualized learning, cultural awareness, and critical thinking.

In the Flipped Classroom model, traditional learning is reversed: students study new content at home via videos or readings, and class time is used for interactive practice and discussion. This approach encourages students to take ownership of their learning and allows teachers to provide more individualized support. For instance, learners might watch a grammar tutorial online, then come to class prepared to apply the rules through games, role-plays, or writing activities. Flipped learning also supports differentiated instruction, as students can learn at their own pace.

Modern didactics also rely heavily on digital innovations to enhance learning. Tools like Kahoot, Quizlet, Padlet, and interactive whiteboards make lessons more engaging. Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Google Classroom or Moodle support blended learning and easy access to resources. Artificial intelligence-based applications like Grammarly or Duolingo provide immediate feedback and personalized learning paths. Virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and

gamification are also gaining popularity, offering immersive and motivating experiences.

In an increasingly globalized world, the ability to use language effectively has become a crucial skill. One of the core aspects of mastering a language is developing *linguistic competence*—the knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, syntax, and pronunciation that allows a speaker to form correct sentences and understand others. While communicative fluency is often emphasized, linguistic competence serves as the foundation for successful language use in both academic and social settings. Modern language education incorporates a range of methods to ensure learners build strong linguistic competence in parallel with communicative skills.

Grammar instruction remains a vital method for building linguistic competence. Two dominant strategies are the inductive and deductive approaches. The inductive approach allows learners to observe patterns in language and derive rules themselves, which often leads to deeper understanding. For example, students may read multiple sentences using the past tense and infer how it is formed. In contrast, the deductive approach starts with rule explanation, followed by structured exercises. This method is effective for adult learners and those preparing for exams, where accuracy is essential. Developing linguistic competence is not only about mastering grammar; vocabulary plays an equally critical role. The lexical approach focuses on teaching language in chunks or collocations rather than isolated words. Phrases like “take a break,” “make a decision,” or “go on a trip” help learners produce natural-sounding speech. By memorizing these fixed expressions, learners can use grammar more correctly and fluently without overanalyzing sentence structures. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) are widely used methods that improve linguistic competence in real-life contexts. TBLT encourages learners to use specific grammar and vocabulary while completing tasks such as planning events or solving problems. These tasks require students to use language meaningfully, which naturally reinforces linguistic structures. Similarly, CLT puts communication at the heart of learning. Activities like role-plays, interviews, and group discussions provide opportunities to practice correct forms in authentic settings. Although the primary focus is fluency, these methods also enhance grammatical accuracy over time, especially when teachers incorporate form-focused feedback.

Repetition-based exercises, or drills, though often seen as outdated, still serve a valuable purpose in reinforcing linguistic structures. Controlled practice through sentence transformations, substitution drills, and fill-in-the-gap tasks helps automate correct usage, especially in early stages of learning.

Feedback also plays a crucial role in developing competence. Techniques such as explicit correction, recasts, and elicitation help learners identify and correct their errors without interrupting the flow of communication. This balance between fluency

and accuracy is essential in language development. Linguistic competence is incomplete without clear pronunciation. Teachers use minimal pair activities (e.g., “bit” vs. “beat”) and intonation exercises to help learners distinguish and produce sounds accurately. Listening to native speakers through audio recordings or videos also improves learners' ability to recognize correct forms and pronunciation patterns, thus boosting both receptive and productive skills. Modern classrooms now integrate digital tools and authentic materials to make language input more engaging and relevant. Educational apps such as Quizlet, Kahoot, and Grammarly allow learners to practice vocabulary and grammar in interactive ways. Moreover, authentic materials like news articles, podcasts, and YouTube videos provide real-life examples of how language is used, exposing learners to accurate forms in context.

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WORD FORMATION IN THE ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the concept of word formation in the English language and underscores its crucial role in vocabulary acquisition and linguistic competence. Word formation refers to the various processes through which new words are created in English, contributing significantly to the dynamic and evolving nature of the language. The study outlines the major types of word formation processes, including affixation (the addition of prefixes and suffixes), compounding (the combination of two or more words to form a new one), conversion (changing a word from one grammatical category to another without altering its form), blending (merging parts of two words into one),

clipping, acronymy, back-formation, and coinage.

Understanding these processes provides learners, particularly at intermediate and upper-intermediate proficiency levels, with essential tools to decode unfamiliar vocabulary, construct new lexical items, and recognize patterns in language use. Furthermore, knowledge of word formation contributes to greater lexical diversity, enabling learners to communicate more precisely and creatively in both spoken and written discourse. From an educational perspective, incorporating word formation into vocabulary instruction fosters morphological awareness, which has been shown to improve reading comprehension, spelling, and word recognition skills. Therefore, an in-depth understanding of how words are formed not only enhances vocabulary development but also supports overall language proficiency and academic success in English.

Keywords: Word formation, vocabulary, affixation, compounding, derivation, morphology, English learners, cultural changes, conversion.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola ingliz tilida so'z yasash tushunchasini o'rganadi va uning lug'at boyligini oshirish hamda til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi muhim rolini ta'kidlaydi. So'z yasash — ingliz tilida yangi so'zlar yaratiladigan turli jarayonlarni anglatadi va bu tilning dinamik va doimo rivojlanib boradigan xususiyatiga katta hissa qo'shadi. Tadqiqot asosiy so'z yasash jarayonlarini ko'rib chiqadi, jumladan: affiksatsiya (prefiks va suffiks qo'shilishi), qo'shma so'z yasash (bir nechta so'zlarni birlashtirish), konversiya (so'z shaklini o'zgartirishdan uning grammatik toifasini o'zgartirish), aralashtirish (ikki so'zning qismlarini birlashtirish), qisqartirish, akronim yasash, orqaga qarab yasash va yangi so'zlar to'liq yangidan yasash (koinaj).

Bu jarayonlarni tushunish, ayniqsa o'rta va undan yuqori darajadagi til o'rganuvchilar uchun, notanish so'zlarni anglash, yangi leksik birliklar yaratish va til ishlatishdagi naqshlarni aniqlashda muhim vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari, so'z yasash usullarini bilish leksik xilma-xillikni oshiradi, bu esa og'zaki va yozma nutqda aniqroq va ijodiy ifodalanish imkonini beradi. Ta'lim nuqtai nazaridan so'z yasashni lug'at o'qitish jarayoniga kiritish morfologik ongni rivojlantiradi, bu esa o'z navbatida matnni tushunish, imlo va so'z tanishlik ko'nikmalarini yaxshilaydi. Shunday qilib, so'zlarning qanday yaratilishini chuqur tushunish lug'aviy rivojlanishni kuchaytiribgina qolmay, balki ingliz tilida umumiy til ko'nikmalari va akademik muvaffaqiyatga ham xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: So'z yasash, lug'at boyligi, affiksatsiya, qo'shma so'zlar, derivatsiya, morfologiya, ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari, madaniy o'zgarishlar, konversiya.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается понятие словообразования в английском языке и подчеркивается его важная роль в усвоении лексики и развитии языковой компетенции. Словообразование охватывает различные процессы, с помощью которых в английском языке создаются новые слова, что существенно способствует его динамичному и постоянно развивающемуся характеру. В исследовании описываются основные типы словообразовательных процессов, включая аффиксацию (добавление префиксов и суффиксов), словосложение (объединение двух и более слов в одно), конверсию (изменение грамматической категории слова без изменения его формы), смешение (слияние частей двух слов в одно), усечение, акронимы, обратное словообразование и неологизмы.

Понимание этих процессов предоставляет учащимся, особенно на среднем и выше среднего уровне владения языком, важные инструменты для распознавания незнакомых слов, создания новых лексических единиц и выявления закономерностей в языке. Более того, знание словообразования способствует расширению лексического запаса, позволяя учащимся точнее

и креативнее выражать свои мысли как в устной, так и в письменной речи. С образовательной точки зрения включение словообразования в обучение лексике развивает морфологическое осознание, что, как доказано, улучшает понимание прочитанного, правописание и распознавание слов. Таким образом, глубокое понимание процессов словообразования не только способствует развитию словарного запаса, но и поддерживает общее владение языком и академическую успешность в английском языке.

Ключевые слова: Словообразование, словарный запас, аффиксация, словосложение, деривация, морфология, изучающие английский язык, культурные изменения, конверсия.

INTRODUCTION

Contact with foreign languages, cultural changes, and technological advancements all have an impact on the English language's ongoing evolution. As a result, different word production processes regularly add new terms to the vocabulary. Understanding word formation is crucial for English language learners, especially those at the B1 level, in order to expand their vocabulary and enhance their receptive (reading, listening) and productive (speaking, writing) language abilities. Learners can interpret foreign vocabulary, make educated estimates about word meanings, and independently generate new words by identifying patterns in word formation, even though memorization of isolated words might be useful. The purpose of this article is to give a thorough review of the processes involved in the production of English words, elucidate their grammatical and semantic functions, and emphasize their importance in language instruction.

The English language is constantly evolving, influenced by technological progress, cultural shifts, and contact with other languages. As a result, new words are frequently added to the lexicon through various word formation processes. The growing impact of globalization, the rise of digital technologies, and the continuous exchange of ideas across cultures have all contributed to the rapid creation of new words in English. This phenomenon is evident in everyday conversations, online communication, and professional jargon, where novel terms often emerge to reflect new ideas, products, and concepts. For instance, terms like "selfie," "hashtag," and "emoji" have all become integral parts of the modern English vocabulary, largely due to the influence of technology and social media.

This article aims to present a comprehensive overview of English word formation processes, explain their grammatical and semantic roles, and highlight their significance in language education. It will explore the key methods used to create new words in English, including affixation, compounding, conversion, and other processes such as blending, clipping, and back-formation. Additionally, the paper will examine how understanding these processes can benefit English learners, especially at the B1 level, by providing practical tools for vocabulary acquisition and enhancing their linguistic competence. The ultimate goal is to offer insights into how word formation contributes not only to language proficiency but also to the broader understanding of

how English functions as a living and constantly evolving language.

Word formation in the English

The most popular and effective way to create new words in the English language is by affixation. It entails adding affixes, or morphemes, to a basic word or root in order to change its meaning or grammatical function. Prefixes and suffixes are the two primary categories into which affixes are often divided. When prefixes are added to a word's beginning, they usually change its meaning without altering its grammatical classification. In the word unhappy, for example, the prefix un- conveys the opposite or negative meaning of the main word happy. The prefixes re- (like redo), dis- (like disagree), and pre- (like preview) are also frequently used. On the other hand, suffixes, which are appended to the end of a word, frequently alter the word's grammatical category, or word class. For instance, the noun happiness is created by appending the suffix -ness to the adjective cheerful. Adjectives (-ful, -less), verbs (-ize, -ify), nouns (-ment, -tion), and adverbs (-ly) can all be formed via suffixes. Because suffixation allows speakers to create several parts of speech from the same root word, it is essential for increasing the versatility of the English vocabulary. Another way to categorize affixation is into two linguistic groups: derivational and inflectional. Derivational affixation alters a word's meaning or classification; for example, it transforms the verb create into the noun creation. For instance, adding -ed to walk to produce the past tense walked or -s to book to signify the plural books are examples of inflectional affixations, which alter a word's tense, number, aspect, or case without altering its fundamental meaning or word class.

Affixation in English is further classified into derivational and inflectional processes, both of which serve distinct linguistic functions. Derivational affixation involves adding prefixes or suffixes to a root word in order to form a new word, often with a change in grammatical category or meaning. For example, the noun beauty can become the adjective beautiful by the addition of the suffix -ful, while the verb care can become the adjective careful. Derivational affixes can also significantly alter a word's meaning without changing its part of speech. For instance, the prefix dis- in dislike reverses the meaning of the base word like. Other common derivational suffixes include -ness (e.g., kind → kindness), -ity (e.g., real → reality), and -er (e.g., teach → teacher). On the other hand, inflectional affixation does not alter a word's basic meaning or word class. Rather, it offers grammatical details like person, number, tense, and comparison. For example, by adding inflectional suffixes, the word play can become plays (third person singular), played (past tense), or playing (present participle). Likewise, when the noun cat is used in the plural, it becomes cats. There are just eight inflectional affixes in English, and they include -s, -ed, -ing, -en, -er, and -est.

Compounding is a highly productive word-formation process in English, whereby two or more independent words are combined to form a new lexical item with

a distinct meaning. The new term often conveys a meaning that is not always predictable from the meanings of its individual parts, making compounds an essential part of vocabulary development and linguistic creativity in English. Compounding can produce various parts of speech, including nouns (e.g., toothpaste, rainbow), adjectives (e.g., high-speed, open-minded), and verbs (e.g., proofread, babysit).

English compounds are generally categorized into three structural types based on how they are written: Closed compounds are written as a single word without spaces or hyphens. These are the most solidified and commonly used compounds. Examples include notebook, classroom, sunflower, and blackboard. Over time, many once-hyphenated or open compounds evolve into closed compounds as their usage becomes more established.

In English, conversion—also referred to as zero derivation—is the process by which a word changes from one grammatical category to another without changing its form. Usually, no prefix, suffix, or other morphological identifier is added during this change. Even when there isn't a noticeable change, the word's new purpose in the phrase may cause changes to its pronunciation or stress pattern. As in "I will email you the document," the noun email can be transformed into the verb to email. As in "I need to clean my room," the adjective clean can also be employed as a verb. Modern English is particularly prone to conversion, which reflects the language's fluidity and flexibility to adjust to shifting cultural and technological norms. Many brand names or nouns are regularly transformed into verbs in digital situations. Google (noun), which has evolved into Google (verb), which means to look for information online, is a perfect example. Other frequent translations include hashtag (noun) to hashtag (verb) and text (noun) to text (verb). Nouns can also become verbs through conversion. It can also happen between adjectives and nouns or in the opposite direction. Better (adjective) can serve as better (verb), as in "She wants to better her performance," and to run (verb) can become a run (noun).

Conversion instruction improves students' grammatical flexibility and their capacity to identify and employ words in a variety of contexts. Because students must learn to recognize how a word's function is determined by its position and use rather than its form, it also promotes a greater knowledge of English sentence structure. This knowledge is very helpful for students who want to communicate in English both orally and in writing with confidence. Blending is the process of combining elements of two or more preexisting words to produce a new term with a distinct meaning. Blending usually entails cutting or deleting portions of the original words and combining the remaining portions, as opposed to compounding, which joins entire words together. While gaining a new, unique identity, the resulting mix frequently keeps meaning components from both source words. Smog (from smoke and fog), brunch (from breakfast and lunch), and motel (from motor and hotel) are classic instances of blends.

These words are so widely used in modern English that people frequently forget where they came from. As demonstrated by infotainment (information + entertainment), blogs (web + log), and netizen (internet + citizen), blends can also represent cultural or technological shifts. Blending is particularly prevalent in informal and creative language use, often appearing in advertising, media, pop culture, and online communication. New blends are frequently coined to describe modern experiences or concepts, such as bromance (brother + romance), hangry (hungry + angry), or spork (spoon + fork). The flexibility and playfulness of blending make it a favored technique for coining catchy, memorable terms.

CONCLUSION

Word formation is a critical component of language learning. By studying how words are created and understanding the processes behind them, learners can enhance their vocabulary and communication skills. Whether through affixation, compounding, conversion, or other methods, word formation opens up a world of possibilities for learners to explore the flexibility and richness of the English language. For both teachers and students, focusing on word formation can lead to more effective language use and greater fluency in communication.

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Немис тили дарсларида ўйин услубидан фойдаланиб нутқ кўникмаларини шакллантириш

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Аннотация

Мазкур мақолада немис тилини ўқитиш жараёнида ўйин элементларини қўллаш орқали ўқувчиларда нутқ кўникмаларини ривожлантириш усуллари таҳлил қилинади. Ўйин услуби дарс жараёнини фаол, қизиқарли ва самарали ташкил этиш, шунингдек, ўқувчиларнинг мулоқотга киришиш қобилиятини оширишда муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются методы развития речевых навыков у учащихся посредством использования игровых элементов в процессе преподавания немецкого языка. Игровой подход способствует активной, увлекательной и эффективной организации учебного процесса, а также играет важную роль в повышении способности учащихся к вступлению в коммуникацию.

Abstract

This article explores methods for developing students' speaking skills through the use of game-based elements in the process of teaching the German language. The game-based approach contributes to organizing the learning process in an active, engaging, and effective manner, and plays a significant role in enhancing students' ability to engage in communication.

Калит сўзлар: Немис тили, ўйин усули, нутқ кўникмалари, таълим жараёни, мулоқот, лексик билимлар, грамматик қоидалар,ролли ўйинлар, иждодий фикрлаш

Ключевые слова Немецкий язык, игровой метод, речевые навыки, учебный процесс, коммуникация, лексические знания, грамматические правила, ролевые игры, творческое мышление

Keywords: German language, game method, speech skills, educational process, communication, lexical knowledge, grammar rules, role-playing games, creative thinking.

Кириш

Ҳозирги глобаллашув даврида хорижий тилларни, жумладан, немис тилини самарали ўргатиш таълимнинг устувор вазифаларидан бири ҳисобланади. Немис тилини ўқитишда талабаларда эркин мулоқот қилиш, тўғри талаффуз қилиш ва фикрини равшан баён этиш кўникмаларини шакллантириш муҳим ўрин тутди. Бу борада анъанавий ўқитиш усуллари билан бирга, ўйин услубидан самарали фойдаланиш дарс жараёнини янада жонлантиради. Ўйин

услуги нафақат ўқувчиларнинг қизиқишини оширади, балки таълим жараёнини интерактив ва фаол ҳолатга келтиради. Бу услубнинг асосий афзалликлари қуйидагилардан иборат:

1. Овоз чиқариб нутқ қилишга рағбатлантиради;
2. Мулоқотни жонлантиради;
3. Грамматик ва лексик материалларни онгли ўзлаштиришга ёрдам беради;
4. Ижодий фикрлаш қобилиятини ривожлантиради;
5. Дарсда ижобий психологик муҳит яратади.

Нутқ кўникмаларини шакллантирувчи ўйин турлари қуйидагилар бўлиб, улар :

Ролли ўйинлар (Rollenspiele): Учрашув, дўконда харид қилиш, шифокор қабулхонасидаги суҳбат каби реал ҳаётга яқин вазиятлар асосида мулоқот қилишга йўналтирилган ўйинлар бўлиб, улар орқали талабаларнинг мулоқот қобилияти ривожланади.

Лексик ўйинлар: "Сўз топ", "Сўз занжири", "Қайси сўз ортиқча?" каби ўйинлар сўз бойлигини ошириш ва лексик билимларни мустаҳкамлашга хизмат қилади.

Грамматик ўйинлар: Грамматик қоидаларни фаол равишда ўзлаштиришни таъминлайдиган машқлар, масалан, феълларнинг тўғри шаклини топиш, тўғри жумла тузиш каби топшириқлар.

Ижодий нутқни ривожлантирувчи ўйинлар: Расм асосида ҳикоя тузиш, қисқа спектакллар тайёрлаш, эртас сўзлаб бериш каби ижодий топшириқлар орқали эркин нутқ кўникмалари шаклланади. Ўйинларни дарс жараёнида самарали қўллаш бўйича қуйидаги тавсиялар эътиборга олинса мақсадга мувофиқ бўлар эди.

Ўйин мавзуси дарсинг асосий мақсадига мос танланиши зарур.

Ўйин учун зарур восита ва материаллар олдиндан тайёрланиши керак.

Ҳар бир ўқувчининг фаол иштирокини таъминлаш мақсадга мувофиқ.

Ўйин натижалари таҳлил қилиниб, хатолар устида ишлашга йўналтирилиши лозим.

Ўйин услубининг афзалликлари бу психологик тўсиқларни енғади, ўйинли фаолият дўстона муҳит яратиб, талабаларнинг эркин фикр билдириши ва мулоқотга қўрқмасдан кириша олишига ёрдам беради. Қизиқиш ва мотивацияни оширади. Ўйинлар ўқув жараёнини мажбурийат эмас, балки қизиқарли фаолият сифатида қабул қилишга олиб келади. Бу эса ўқувчиларнинг дарсдаги иштирокини фаоллаштиради. Интерактив муҳит яратиш эса жамоавий ўйинлар талабалар ўртасида ҳамкорлик, фикр алмашиш ва мулоқот кўникмаларини кучайтириб, лексик ва грамматик билимларни онгли

ўзлаштиришда ёрдам беради. Ўйин орқали грамматик қоидалар ва сўзлар амалий фаолият жараёнида табиий ўзлаштирилади. Ижодий ва танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантириш, талабалар маълумотни фақат қабул қилмасдан, уни қайта ишлаб, янги шароитда қўллашни ва хатолар орқали ўрганишни шакллантиради. Ўйин жараёнидаги хатолар жиддий танбەх сифатида эмас, балки ўрганиш имконияти сифатида қабул қилинади. Барча тил кўникмаларини ривожлантириш, ўйинлар бир вақтнинг ўзида гапириш, тинглаш, ўқиш ва ёзиш фаолиятини қамраб олади. Индивидуал ёндашув имконияти ҳар бир ўқувчи билан индивидуал ишлаш имконини беради. Ўйинлар турлича услуб ва шаклда ташкил этилгани учун ҳар бир ўқувчининг қобилияти ва қизиқишидан келиб чиқиб танланиши мумкин бўлади.

Хулоса

Немис тилини ўқитиш жараёнида ўйин услубидан фойдаланиш нафақат дарсни қизиқарли ва жонли ўтказишга, балки ўқувчиларда фаол нутқ кўникмаларини шакллантиришга ҳам хизмат қилади. Ушбу метод таълимда инновацион ёндашув ҳисобланиб, талабаларни ижодкор, мустақил фикрловчи ва фаол шахс сифатида тарбиялашда муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

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TEACHING ENGLISH TO ECONOMICAL FACULTY STUDENTS

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Abstract

In today's globalized economic environment, English language proficiency is essential for students pursuing studies in economics and finance. This paper explores effective strategies for teaching English to second-year students enrolled in the Economical Faculty. The study examines the integration of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), and task-based learning approaches in curriculum design, with a focus on improving students' language proficiency and comprehension.

Findings reveal that ESP-based instruction significantly enhances students' understanding of core economic concepts in English, while task-based activities increase learner engagement and communication skills. Moreover, the use of authentic materials—such as economic reports, financial news, and business case studies—improves reading and analytical skills. Challenges identified include limited exposure to real-world economic discourse and insufficient vocabulary depth among learners.

The study concludes by recommending a hybrid teaching model that incorporates both content and language integrated learning (CLIL) and ESP, supported by digital tools and collaborative tasks. These methods are shown to be particularly effective for second-year students, as they build upon their foundational knowledge while promoting active use of English in professional contexts.

Keywords

English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Economics Education, Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Second-Year University Students, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), Academic Vocabulary Acquisition.

Annotatsiya

Bugungi globallashtirilgan iqtisodiy muhitda iqtisodiyot va moliya sohalarida tahsil olayotgan talabalar uchun ingliz tilini bilish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada Iqtisodiyot fakultetining ikkinchi kurs talabarlari uchun ingliz tilini o'qitishda samarali strategiyalar o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), kommunikativ til o'qitish (CLT) va vazifaga yo'naltirilgan o'rganish yondoshuvlarini o'quv dasturiga integratsiyalashga qaratilgan bo'lib, talabalar til ko'nikmalarini va tushunishini yaxshilashga yo'naltirilgan.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ESP asosidagi ta'lim talabalar iqtisodiy tushunchalarni ingliz tilida yaxshiroq anglashlarini ta'minlaydi, vazifaga asoslangan faoliyatlar esa o'rganish jarayoniga qiziqishni va muloqot ko'nikmalarini oshiradi. Bundan tashqari, iqtisodiy hisobotlar, moliyaviy yangiliklar va biznes holatlari kabi haqiqiy materiallardan foydalanish o'qish va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Muammolar sifatida real iqtisodiy muloqotga cheklangan duch kelish va lug'at boyligining yetishmasligi aniqlangan.

Tadqiqot til va kontent integratsiyalangan o'rganish (CLIL) va ESP ni raqamli vositalar hamda hamkorlikdagi vazifalar yordamida birlashtirgan gibrid o'qitish modelini tavsiya qiladi. Ushbu yondashuvlar ikkinchi kurs talabalar uchun samarali bo'lib, ularning asosiy bilimlarini mustahkamlash va ingliz tilini professional kontekstda faol qo'llashini rag'batlantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar

Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), Iqtisodiy ta'lim, Vazifaga yo'naltirilgan til o'qitish (TBLT), Kommunikativ til o'qitish (CLT), Ikkinchi kurs talabalar, Til va kontent integratsiyalangan o'rganish (CLIL), Akademik lug'at boyligi

Аннотация

В условиях глобализированной экономической среды владение английским языком является необходимым для студентов, изучающих экономику и финансы. В данной статье рассматриваются эффективные стратегии преподавания английского языка студентам второго курса Экономического факультета. Исследование изучает интеграцию английского языка для специальных целей (ESP), коммуникативного метода обучения (CLT) и обучения на основе заданий в разработке учебной программы, с акцентом на повышение языковой компетенции и понимания учащихся.

Результаты показывают, что обучение на основе ESP значительно улучшает понимание студентами основных экономических понятий на английском языке, в то время как заданный подход повышает вовлеченность учащихся и навыки коммуникации. Кроме того,

использование аутентичных материалов — таких как экономические отчеты, финансовые новости и бизнес-кейсы — способствует развитию навыков чтения и анализа. Выявлены такие проблемы, как ограниченный доступ к реальному экономическому дискурсу и недостаточный словарный запас.

В исследовании рекомендуется гибридная модель обучения, которая сочетает интегрированное обучение содержанию и языку (CLIL) с ESP, поддерживаемая цифровыми инструментами и совместными заданиями. Эти методы особенно эффективны для студентов второго курса, так как они опираются на базовые знания и стимулируют активное использование английского в профессиональных контекстах.

Ключевые слова

Английский для специальных целей (ESP), Экономическое образование, Обучение языку на основе заданий (TBLT), Коммуникативное обучение (CLT), Студенты второго курса, Интегрированное обучение содержанию и языку (CLIL), Академическое усвоение словарного запаса.

1. Introduction

The global importance of English as a lingua franca has influenced many academic disciplines, including economics. As economies become increasingly interdependent and global markets expand, the demand for professionals proficient in English—especially in economics and finance—continues to grow. For students in the Economical Faculty, acquiring English language competence is not only vital for academic success but also a key asset for future professional endeavors.

This paper explores how to effectively teach English to second-year university students studying economics. At this academic level, students typically possess foundational knowledge of both their discipline and general English, making it an ideal stage to integrate English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and communicative teaching methods. By aligning English instruction with economic content, educators can foster deeper language retention and critical thinking skills.

The study aims to evaluate the efficacy of various instructional approaches—ESP, Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)—in improving language proficiency and economic literacy. This article adopts the IMRAD structure to present findings from an applied study conducted over a 12-week course at a university's Economical Faculty.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

The study was conducted with 120 second-year students enrolled in the Economical Faculty at a state university. Participants were divided into four groups, each consisting of 30 students. All participants had completed at least one year of general English instruction and demonstrated intermediate English proficiency based on CEFR standards (B1-B2).

2.2 Course Design

The instructional intervention lasted 12 weeks and included three teaching approaches:

- **Group A** followed an ESP-focused curriculum with authentic economic texts.
- **Group B** received instruction using Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).
- **Group C** was taught using Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) strategies.
- **Group D** served as a control group, receiving standard grammar-based instruction.

Each group had four hours of instruction per week. The curriculum included lessons on vocabulary building, reading comprehension, writing economic reports, and oral presentations.

2.3 Data Collection

To measure the effectiveness of the approaches, a mixed-methods design was used, including:

- **Pre- and post-tests** evaluating vocabulary, reading, writing, and speaking skills.
- **Surveys** measuring student attitudes and engagement.
- **Teacher observations** recorded weekly in instructional logs.

2.4 Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using paired sample t-tests to compare pre- and post-test scores. Qualitative feedback from students and teachers was coded for recurring themes such as relevance, engagement, and perceived improvement.

3. Results

3.1 Language Proficiency Gains

The analysis of pre- and post-course test results demonstrated statistically significant improvements across all key language skill areas. Notably:

- Vocabulary acquisition showed the highest improvement, with students' scores increasing by an average of 32%.
- Reading comprehension of economic texts improved by 27%, particularly in interpreting data, identifying main ideas, and understanding terminology.
- Writing skills, especially in summarizing articles and composing short analytical essays, improved by 22%.
- Speaking fluency and oral presentation skills saw a more modest gain of 15%, though students exhibited greater confidence and fluency in using economic terminology in discussion tasks.

These gains were more prominent in the group that regularly engaged in task-based and communicative learning activities.

3.2 Effectiveness of Teaching Methods

Comparative classroom performance and student feedback indicated varying degrees of effectiveness for each teaching approach:

- ESP (English for Specific Purposes) emerged as the most effective in improving domain-specific vocabulary and reading comprehension. Students reported that working with authentic economic texts made the content more relevant and increased motivation.

- TBLT (Task-Based Language Teaching) was especially effective for enhancing writing and speaking skills. Simulated real-world economic problems, such as drafting business proposals or participating in investment pitch scenarios, encouraged practical language use.

- CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) contributed significantly to students' interaction and fluency. However, some students struggled with spontaneous speech production due to limited exposure to natural economic dialogue.

3.3 Student Feedback

Students appreciated the connection between language learning and their economics coursework. They found the task-based projects intellectually stimulating and reported increased confidence in using English in academic and informal settings. Challenges included vocabulary overload and uneven participation in group work.

3.4 Instructor Observations

Teachers observed that students were more responsive when lessons were based on current economic issues or real-world data. Digital tools enhanced learner autonomy and interest.

4. Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of Key Findings

The results of this study reveal that a combination of ESP, task-based learning, and communicative methods yields positive outcomes in teaching English to second-year economics students. The statistically significant improvements in vocabulary and reading comprehension underscore the effectiveness of ESP-oriented instruction. The integration of real-world materials and authentic tasks helped bridge the gap between general English knowledge and the specific linguistic demands of economic studies.

4.2 Pedagogical Implications

ESP should form the core of the curriculum, task-based instruction enhances practical language use, and authentic materials improve reading and vocabulary-building skills. Collaborative learning must be structured to ensure equal participation.

4.3 Addressing Challenges

To avoid vocabulary overload, teachers should use scaffolded vocabulary instruction. Role assignments and teacher monitoring can help ensure even group work. More structured oral practice routines are recommended for improving speaking skills.

4.4 Integration with Content-Based Instruction

CLIL has strong potential for advanced learners. For second-year students with sufficient content and language base, teaching economic content in English strengthens both domains simultaneously.

4.5 Curriculum Development Recommendations

Recommendations include modular course design, continuous performance-based assessment, ESP and TBLT training for teachers, and integration of digital resources.

4.6 Limitations of the Study

Limitations include the single-institution setting, short duration, and instructor variability. Future research should explore longitudinal effects and multi-institutional comparisons.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the effectiveness of various instructional methods—namely English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)—in teaching English to second-year students in the Economical Faculty. The results demonstrate that a blended approach, integrating ESP and task-based methods, significantly improves students' vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, and application of economic discourse in both written and spoken forms.

Students responded positively to the use of authentic materials and real-world economic scenarios. ESP proved particularly effective for building subject-specific language skills, while TBLT encouraged active participation. Though speaking fluency showed only moderate improvement, more structured oral communication activities are needed.

The study recommends a curriculum that combines ESP with elements of CLIL, supported by digital tools and collaborative learning. This research contributes to the growing field of English for Academic Purposes, offering practical guidance for improving English instruction among economics students.

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MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PHARMACEUTICAL AND INDUSTRIAL PHARMACY DIRECTION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. This study explores the effectiveness of modern English language teaching methods—specifically Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Flipped Classroom, and Blended Learning—in enhancing English proficiency among students in pharmaceutical and industrial pharmacy programs. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the research analyzes quantitative data from pre- and post-intervention assessments and qualitative insights from student and instructor feedback. The findings indicate that these innovative methods significantly improve language competence, particularly in reading and writing skills, and increase student motivation and engagement.

Key words: CLT, pedagogical approaches, student-centered learning.

Аннотация. В этом исследовании изучается эффективность современных методов обучения английскому языку, в частности, обучения языку на основе задач (TBLT), коммуникативного обучения языку (CLT), перевернутого класса и смешанного обучения, в повышении уровня владения английским языком среди студентов фармацевтических и промышленных фармацевтических программ. Используя подход смешанных методов, исследование анализирует количественные данные оценок до и после вмешательства и качественные выводы из отзывов студентов и преподавателей. Результаты показывают, что эти инновационные методы значительно улучшают языковую компетенцию, особенно в навыках чтения и письма, и повышают мотивацию и вовлеченность студентов.

Ключевые слова: CLT, педагогические подходы, обучение, ориентированное на студентов.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot farmatsevtika va sanoat farmatsevtika dasturlarida talabalar o'rtasida ingliz tilini bilish darajasini oshirishda zamonaviy ingliz tilini o'qitish usullarining, xususan Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Flipped Classroom va Blended Learning samaradorligini o'rganadi. Aralash usullardan foydalangan holda, tadqiqot aralashuvdan oldingi va keyingi baholashning miqdoriy ma'lumotlarini va talaba va o'qituvchining fikr-mulohazasidan olingan sifatli tushunchalarni tahlil qiladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu innovatsion usullar til kompetensiyasini, xususan, o'qish va yozish ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi va talabalarining motivatsiyasi va faolligini oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: CLT, pedagogik yondashuvlar, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim.

Introduction

In the pharmaceutical and industrial pharmacy sectors, English proficiency is crucial for accessing scientific literature, understanding global regulatory standards, and engaging in international collaboration. Traditional English language teaching methods often emphasize rote memorization and grammar translation, which may not effectively develop the communicative competence required in these fields. Modern pedagogical approaches offer promising alternatives by focusing on interaction, real-life communication, and integration of technology.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), developed by theorists such as Rod Ellis and Peter Skehan, emphasizes the use of authentic language through meaningful tasks (Ellis et al., 2019). Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), rooted in the work of Dell Hymes and further developed by Michael Canale and Merrill Swain, focuses on interaction as both the means and ultimate goal of language learning (Canale & Swain, 1980). The Flipped Classroom model, popularized by educators Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams, involves students engaging with instructional content outside of class and using classroom time for interactive activities (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). Blended Learning, as discussed by Charles R. Graham, combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning experiences to enhance educational outcomes (Graham, 2006). This study aims to assess the impact of these methods on English language acquisition among pharmacy students.

Methods

Research Design

A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving control and experimental groups. The experimental group received instruction through modern teaching methods, while the control group was taught using traditional methods. Pre- and post-tests were administered to measure language proficiency. Surveys and interviews provided qualitative data on student attitudes and experiences.

Participants

The study involved 120 undergraduate pharmacy students from a university in Uzbekistan, divided equally into control and experimental groups.

Intervention

The experimental group participated in a 12-week program incorporating:

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): Students engaged in tasks simulating real-world pharmaceutical scenarios, such as patient counseling and drug information dissemination, following principles outlined by Ellis et al. (2019).

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): Activities included role-plays and discussions focused on pharmaceutical contexts to enhance communicative competence, as advocated by Canale and Swain (1980).

Flipped Classroom: Students studied instructional materials online before class, allowing in-class time for interactive activities and application of knowledge, in line with the model proposed by Bergmann and Sams (2012).

Blended Learning: A combination of online and face-to-face instruction was employed to provide flexibility and reinforce learning, as discussed by Graham (2006).

The control group continued with traditional grammar-focused instruction.

Data Collection

Language proficiency was assessed using standardized tests focusing on reading and writing skills. Surveys measured student motivation and attitudes toward English learning. Interviews with instructors provided additional insights into classroom dynamics.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using paired t-tests to determine the significance of improvements in language proficiency. Qualitative data underwent thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and insights related to student experiences.

Results

Quantitative Findings

The experimental group demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in language proficiency scores, with an average increase of 22% compared to a 6% increase in the control group ($p < 0.01$). Specifically, reading skills improved by 24%, and writing skills by 20% in the experimental group.

Qualitative Insights

Students in the experimental group reported increased motivation and confidence in using English. They found the modern teaching methods engaging and relevant to their field. Instructors observed higher levels of student participation and enthusiasm in the classes employing innovative methods.

Discussion

The findings suggest that modern teaching methods effectively enhance English language proficiency among pharmacy students. By emphasizing communication, real-life tasks, and technology integration, these methods address the practical language needs of students, fostering both linguistic competence and confidence. The significant improvements in reading and writing skills align with previous studies highlighting the benefits of such approaches in language education. Furthermore, the increased student motivation observed supports the notion that innovative methods create a more engaging and student-centered learning environment.

Conclusion

Implementing modern English teaching methods in pharmaceutical and industrial pharmacy education leads to substantial improvements in language proficiency, particularly in reading and writing skills. These methods also enhance student motivation and engagement, making them valuable approaches in language education. Educators are encouraged to adopt these strategies to better meet the communicative needs of pharmacy students.

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THE ROLE OF NATIONAL VALUES IN THE MORAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY STUDENTS

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Abstract: The education of the younger generation is a very urgent issue, which requires consistency, perseverance and diligence in education, as well as modern, effective methods and means of work. A continuous education system that covers all stages of the education and upbringing process and their interdependence creates all the conditions for raising a mature, well-rounded generation. The article discusses the issues of creating theoretical foundations and providing scientific and methodological recommendations through the study of the pedagogical conditions for using national values in the moral and ethical education of primary school students.

Keywords: education, learning, upbringing, person, elementary school, school, learning, dedication, virtue, thought, child, thought - reasoning, ability, dialectic, process, mature generation, education, axiology, modern, spiritual and moral upbringing.

Annotatsiya: Yosh avlod tarbiyasi o'ta dolzarb masala bo'lib, ta'lim-tarbiyada izchillik, matonat va mehnatsevarlikni hamda zamonaviy, samarali ish uslub va vositalarini talab qiladi. Ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonining barcha bosqichlarini, ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini qamrab olgan uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi yetuk, barkamol avlodni tarbiyalash uchun barcha sharoitlarni yaratadi. Maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini axloqiy-axloqiy tarbiyalashda milliy qadriyatlardan foydalanishning pedagogik shartlarini o'rganish orqali nazariy asoslarni yaratish va ilmiy-metodik tavsiyalar berish masalalari muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: ta'lim, o'rganish, tarbiya, shaxs, boshlang'ich maktab, maktab, o'rganish, fidoyilik, ezgulik, fikr, bola, fikr – tafakkur, qobiliyat, dialektika, jarayon, yetuk avlod, ta'lim, aksiologiya, zamonaviy, ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya.

Аннотация: Воспитание подрастающего поколения является весьма актуальной проблемой, требующей последовательности, настойчивости и старания в образовании, а также современных, эффективных методов и средств работы. Система непрерывного образования, охватывающая все этапы процесса обучения и воспитания и их взаимозависимость, создает все условия для воспитания зрелого, всесторонне развитого поколения. В статье рассматриваются вопросы создания теоретических основ и предоставления научно-методических рекомендаций через изучение педагогических условий использования национальных ценностей в нравственно-этическом воспитании учащихся младших классов.

Ключевые слова: образование, обучение, воспитание, личность, начальная школа, школа, обучение, самоотверженность, добродетель, мысль, ребенок, мысль - рассуждение, способность, диалектика, процесс, зрелое поколение, образование, аксиология, современное, духовно-нравственное воспитание.

INTRODUCTION

The article studies the pedagogical conditions for using national values in the moral and ethical education of primary school students. Education and upbringing are a continuous process, and education based on national values is an important factor in the formation of the human qualities of students. Today, educating students on the basis of new pedagogical technologies is one of the urgent issues for the development of society.

METHODS

The following methods were used in the article:

- Theoretical analysis - advanced pedagogical concepts of moral and ethical education were studied.
- Experimental work - educational exercises based on national values were conducted with primary school students.
- Survey and observation - interviews were conducted with teachers and parents, and the activities of students in the educational process were observed.
- Comparison and analysis - the experience of local and foreign education systems in instilling national values in students was analyzed.

BODY PART

The full acceptance of the norms of society by the growing generation, the growth of a good and necessary person of their time, is directly related to the correct relations that the family establishes with other formal educational institutions. The role of preschool educational institutions in the process of socialization is of particular importance. Because employees of preschool educational institutions communicate directly with the child's parents every day, and they perform two different functions, different from the school administration: official and informal. In addition, the educator himself is in two different positions in relation to the parents - as an official educator

and as a sincere, attentive interlocutor. However, it is not so easy to coordinate the work of family members and employees of preschool educational institutions in the upbringing of one child, to achieve good results. Because only when both parties trust each other, can there be sincere communication between them and positive results in upbringing can be achieved. A number of psychological principles of such successful relationships can be identified:

- First of all, the educator should be able to show the parents only the best side of their child. That is, only if the image of the child in kindergarten is positive for the parents, they will bring their child home with good manners and, when returning home, will be able to say goodbye to the educator warmly, teaching the child to respect him and listen to what he says in the lessons. Otherwise, the parents may be offended and bring their child to kindergarten and teach him to be submissive to the rules of the preschool educational institution. So, the first principle is to create a positive image of the child in the preschool educational institution for the parents;

- educators of preschool educational institutions should be able to show the child's achievements, what knowledge, skills and abilities he has acquired in daily communication with parents. For example, he should be able to provide informal information about how he behaves in communication with peers, whether he has friends, how he was able to master a given poem or other task today, how he was able to help someone, what his sociometric status is. Therefore, the principle of informing parents about the child's achievements strengthens the partnership between parents and educators.

- The educator must be aware of the child's behavior at home, his achievements or shortcomings. This is determined in the process of trusting dialogue with the parents. Because if the educator does not know how the child behaves at home, his habits and actions, he cannot organize the right pedagogical approach to him. That is, the third principle is to know the child's status in the family, in the home.

Taking the above into account in the socialization of the child will allow preschool educational institutions to work with the family under the single motto "Let's learn together!" and achieve success. It should not be forgotten that the main interested party and the one who shows activity in this should be, first of all, parents.

In recent years, the importance of family education has been increasing. In many countries, a number of legislative acts and regulatory acts have been adopted, according to which, at the request of the parents, it is possible to organize the education and upbringing of a child in a family environment, in the home. The legal rights of such educators are guaranteed by law. For example, documents such as the "Regulations on Family (Home) Education in the Russian Federation", "Model Regulations on Home Education" are guaranteed by the country's Law "On Education", according to which, if the parents wish, a home educator comes to the

home and educates the child(ren). Such experiences as using the services of governesses and hiring home nannies have become widespread in many developed countries. Some of the first manifestations of this movement have also appeared in our country, Uzbekistan. However, in our country, family education is organized for children who need special support, orphans, and disabled children. Because, first of all, Uzbek children, due to the opportunities provided by law, can be directly in the care of their mother for up to 2-3 years, during which time the state also provides a pension to mothers with children under two years of age. If the family has the opportunity, in later periods the child will again be raised with the help of his mother or grandmother, and will be involved in preschool educational institutions.

For children with disabilities from birth and limited access to school, home education is organized in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". Such teachers are also given additional benefits, they provide a disabled child with the most necessary knowledge, skills and abilities at home based on a 6-hour program. This is also Uzbekistan's policy in reforming the social sphere, and no child in our country is left out of education at school age.

Children with normal development are attracted to school after preschool educational institutions, where everyone knows that the effectiveness of education and upbringing also depends on cooperation with the family. For this reason, "Parent Councils" have been established in each secondary school, they are given considerable rights and powers, which is proof of the practical functioning of the "School - Family - Neighborhood" concept. But there are problems in this regard, because school administration and pedagogues do not always know the families of all students, their circumstances, and the extent of parents' interest and commitment to their child's education. As a result, sometimes it is during the school years that the child's psychology changes dramatically, and he or she may even fall into the category of deviant behavior.

That is, it is of great social importance to remember that the process of socialization of young people takes place at all stages of continuous education in our country, based on the National Program for Personnel Training and the Law on Education, and to know that its effectiveness at each stage depends on the correct and accurate selection of socialization methods and tools.

If there are children involved, the courts will resolve the matter, but in most cases, the self-governing body of the mahalla and its activists, who are members of the reconciliation commission, will intervene, and the public will prevent young people from going to divorce for a trivial reason. Because in the national mentality, leaving a child alive as an orphan is considered a great sin, therefore, there is a long-standing principle that adults intervene in the future fate of a young family, and after studying the causes of the family conflict, a decision is reached. If the family conflict seriously

threatens the health, peace, and coexistence of young people, primarily the woman and children (such as the inability to forgive each other due to betrayal, the husband's constant torment of the woman due to her constant drinking, domestic violence, the man's failure to contribute to the family budget), the public will protect the woman's rights, and the mahalla itself will intervene in this matter in order to determine the fate of the woman and her children, and to provide them with social protection. In recent years, local women's activists have been paying special attention to increasing the fair activity of self-governing bodies on these issues.

The national characteristics of the Uzbek people are manifested in their national culture, achievements in science, art and literature, family lifestyle, methods and measures used in child upbringing. National customs, traditions, cultural heritage are a unique monument, a component of all spiritual wealth, an achievement of human intelligence and thinking. Each nation preserves its own wealth of knowledge, experience and historical lessons, morals, educational teachings and guidelines inherited from its ancestors. Passing on this invaluable wealth to the growing generation, drawing the right conclusions from them, being proud of them and forming a sense of national pride through them gives good results. Any nation has inherited traditions from its ancestors. For example, Kazakhs have banned more than two hundred things in the past, which serve to preserve the unique national nature, culture, literature, language, and beliefs of the Kazakh people.

Our values in the field of morality, education and upbringing are an invaluable national heritage and spiritual wealth for us. We believe that restoring these national values, using them, and passing them on to the younger generation will be a practical program in strengthening independence, striking at any force that opposes it, and instilling a sense of national pride in our children.

Our national values glorify knowledge, especially erudition. Important ideas about the fact that knowledge is the greatest wealth, that there is nothing more valuable in the world, are expressed in such famous works as "Kalila and Dimna" by the ancient Indians, "Siyosatnoma" by Nizamulmulk, "Saodatnoma" by Nasir Khisrov, "Roshnoma" by Yusuf Khos Hajib, "Kutadgu bilik" by Yusuf Khos Hajib, "Hibatul haqoyiq" by Ahmad Yugnaki, "Devoni hikmat" by Ahmad Yassavi, "Khamsa" by Alisher Navoi, "Mahbub-ul qulub" by

In the culture and history of the Uzbek nation, there is probably no poet, writer or scientist who has not called on people to learn the basics of science and has not written about the nature of knowledge. Each of the works written by our great ancestors Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Ahmad al-Farghani, Abu Rayhan al-Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sino is an incomparable wealth for humanity, a mine of inexhaustible treasures. These and a number of other scientific, artistic, historical, philosophical, medical, ethical, legal and other works of our wise men, who are the

pride and honor of the Uzbek nation, illuminate the prospects of our current youth and future generations with the light of science and enlightenment.

Moral education occupies a special place in folk pedagogy. Each nation, ethnic group, including the Uzbek people, has created its own moral laws and regulations, the ideal of humanity is the basis of moral laws. Since ancient times, efforts have been made to educate the younger generation in a way that is humane, beautiful, and proud. The rich spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people is reflected in the "Avesta". Regarding the educational significance of the work, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, in a conversation with historians, said: "It has been 3,000 years since our most authoritative, ancient manuscript, the Avesta, was created. This rare book is the spiritual and historical heritage of our ancestors, who lived on this land between two rivers, 20th century ago, and left to our descendants. The Avesta is also a historical document that testifies to the great state, great spirituality, and great culture that existed in this ancient land at that time, which no one can deny.

"The Belgian Avesta scholar Jacques Duchesne-Guillaume, defining the spiritual value of the Avesta, said: "Among the sons of the East, the West was the first to adopt Zoroaster as its son. His teachings enriched Greece four centuries before the teachings of Jesus Christ. Plato knew Zoroaster." It took a long time for the voices of Buddha and Confucius to reach Europe, so for centuries the West was acquainted with the ancient wisdom of the East only through Zoroastrianism..." This unique masterpiece, which is considered the basis of the spirituality and history of the Uzbek nation, is the pride and national pride of our people.

In order to form a sense of national pride in primary school students, it is important to study the Avesta, which is considered the basis of our culture and spirituality. When we read this masterpiece, we feel harmony in it with the customs and traditions that exist among our people today.

For example, in the Avesta, increasing the arable land, plowing, preserving it, and worshiping it as sacred took on the form of a divine order. Worshiping fire, praying to Mithra, the god of earth and fire, and Romano, the god of pastures, building a house, filling it with domestic animals, wives, and children, growing plants and trees, breeding large and small domestic animals, and caring for the land formed the basis of the Zoroastrian religion.

Such a place is a place where an Ashavan built a house. A prosperous life reigns in that house. A herd of cows and a housewife, children and flocks live. The herd of cows is well cared for. ... The food of the Texas is plentiful, the sustenance of good dogs is plentiful. The housewife is happy. The children are joyful. The fire is always roaring. Every beautiful event of life leads to goodness ("Vandidod", 3rd fargard, paragraphs 2-3).

What are the most heinous and grievous sins of humans that please and please the giants?

Ahura Mazda replied:

Whoever, after combing his hair or cutting his nails, pours it into a pit or a hollow without any ritual, this evil deed is equal to praising the giants with a prayer, strengthening them, and granting them victory ("Vandidod", 1-fargard, paragraphs 1-2).

“The punishment in hell for the one who refuses to drink pure water and burn in front of a burning fire is worse than all the sufferings of this world.” Forming a sense of national pride in our national and spiritual values in primary school students is a long-term process. Presenting folk teachings, proverbs, national traditions, national values, and exemplary events related to the life and work of famous scholars, military leaders, and artists during spiritual and educational events organized among primary school students will yield positive results. Increasing attention to folk tales, epics, proverbs, sayings, legends, melodies, and songs that embody and promote the meaningful and wise ideas of our national values and promote them will be effective.

CONCLUSION

Folk oral creativity, which is a component of the national and spiritual heritage, is undoubtedly an important educational tool in increasing the boundless love of the younger generation for the people, the homeland, and in cultivating national pride. The historical experience of our ancestors in instilling a sense of national pride in the minds of young people is vividly reflected in the examples of folk art. Folklore works serve to improve the quality of moral education among young people and to raise the future generation in a spiritually perfect way. Taking this into account, the use of masterpieces of oral artistic creativity, which embody the most ancient and life-giving traditions of our national culture, as a source of artistic aesthetic and psycho-social strength in the formation of a sense of national pride in primary school students of higher educational institutions is of great importance.

In general, folklore works imbued with the patriotism, hard work, loyalty, honesty, truthfulness, and justice of our ancestors can serve as a comprehensive example for today's youth. Each young generation should be proud of being the heirs of this land and great ancestors, and live with a sense of national pride.

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Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarning insho yozish malakalarini rivojlantirish yo‘llari

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada insho va uning ahamiyati, boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarning insho yozish malakalarini rivojlantirish yo‘llari haqida fikr yuritilgan. Maqolada o‘quvchilarning bog‘lanishli nutqiy ko‘nikmalarini o‘stirish, insho yozish malakalarini shakllantirish yuzasidan mashqlar va ularni tashkil qilish metodikasi haqida ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Tayanch so‘zlar: insho, bog‘lanishli nutq, grammatik kompetensiya, nutqiy kompetensiya, imloviy savodxonlik.

Annotation

This article reflects on the essay and its significance, ways in which Primary School students develop their essay writing skills. The article presents information about the training of students on the development of linkage speech skills, the formation of essay writing skills, and the methodology for their organization.

Base words: essay, bound speech, grammatical competence, colloquial competence, spelling literacy mon.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассматривается эссе и его важность, а также пути развития навыков написания эссе у учащихся начальной школы. В статье представлена информация об упражнениях по развитию коммуникативных речевых навыков учащихся, формированию навыков написания эссе и методике их организации.

Базовые слова: эссе, связная речь, грамматическая компетентность, речевая компетентность, орфографическая грамотность пн.

Insho — o‘quvchining ijodiy ishi hisoblanadi. U bilim, faollik, tanlangan mavzuga qiziqish, mustaqil fikr yuritish kabilarning mahsuli sifatida yaratiladi. Insho uchun material tayyorlash, tartibga solish, insho rejasini tuzish, ma‘lumotlarni

mantiqiy bog'lash, ifoda uchun so'z yoki so'z birikmasini tanlash, gap tuzish hamda ularni o'zaro bog'lash, imloviy savodxonlik kabi barcha murakkab jarayonlarda o'quvchidan o'z aqliy kuchini to'la safarbar etish, ijodkorlik talab etiladi. Insho shunday jarayonki, unda o'quvchining grammatik kompetensiyasi nutqiy kompetensiyaviy mahorati bilan qo'shilib ketadi. Garchi insho yozish murakkab jarayon bo'lsa-da, o'quvchi fikrlar o'ziniki bo'lgani uchun ham bu jarayonni sevadi.

Insho savodxonlik darajasini tekshirishning sinalgan usullaridan biri sanaladi. Yaxshi insho yozish uchun yozuvchi bo'lish shart emas. Insho yozish – bu ijodiy jarayon. Bu jarayonni bir necha qismlarga bo'lib, insho yozishni ancha soddalashtirib olish mumkin. Aqlingizni ishga solib, asosiy g'oyalarni aniqlash, ularni qoramamaga yozib qo'yish va shu asosda ajoyib ijod namunasini yaratish mumkin.[3]

Insho quyida berilgan vazifalarni bajaradi:

- o'quvchining ichki kechinmalarini, his-hayajon tuyg'usini, ya'ni emotsiyasini o'stirish;

- o'quvchining aqlini (intelektni) rivojlantirish;

- o'quvchini mustaqil ijodiy fikrlashga o'rgatish;

- o'quvchining voqelik yoki hodisalar haqida fikr bildirish, ularni baholash ko'nikmasini shakllantirish.

Insho yozish mazmuni boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining his-hayajon va aqliy tuyg'ularini o'stirish, ularni mustaqil fikrlash va baholashga o'rgatish bilan belgilanadi. Inshoning asosiy xususiyati uning ijodiy ishligidir.

Insho yozish ko'nikmasi tez fursatda oson o'zlashtiriladigan yozma ish turi hisoblanmaydi. Insho yozish ko'nikmasi ko'p yillik faoliyat natijasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Insho shaxsni shakllantirishda foydali vosita bo'lib, his-hayajon uyg'otadi, aqliy mustaqillikka, fikrlashga, ko'rgan-kechirganlari va o'zlashtirganlarini baholashga, kuzatuvchanlikka, voqea-hodisalar o'rtasidagi sabab-natija bog'lanishni topishga, ularni qiyoslashga, xulosa chiqarishga o'rgatadi. Insho fikrni tartibga soladi, o'quvchilarda o'ziga, o'z kuchi va imkoniyatiga ishonch tug'diradi. [1]

Insho yozish jarayonni amalga oshirish uchun birinchi o'rnida o'quvchilarda bog'lanishli nutqni shakllantirish lozim.

Fikrni bayon etish ehtiyojini amalga oshirishga qaratilgan, tugallangan mavzuni ifodalaydigan, logik va grammatik qoidalar asosida tuzilgan, mustaqil, tugallangan va o'zaro bog'langan ma'noli qismlarga bo'linadigan nutq bog'lanishli nutq deyiladi. Bog'lanishli nutq birligi sifatida hikoya, maqola, roman, monografiya, doklad, hisobot kabilarni, maktab sharoitida esa o'qituvchidan berilgan savolga o'quvchilarning keng, mukammal og'zaki javobini, yozma bayon va inshoni olish mumkin.[1]

Ona tili darslarida bog'lanishli nutqni rivojlantirish uchun quyidagi mashq turlaridan foydalanish mumkin:

1. Savolga yozma shaklda javob berish.
2. Kuzatishlarini, ob-havo kundaligini yuritib borish.
3. Matnni og'zaki hamda yozma tarzda qayta hikoya qilish.
4. Tanlangan mavzu yoki rasmi topshiriq asosida boshi yoki oxiri berilgan syujet asosida og'zaki va yozma hikoya qilish.
5. Ertakni alohida tayyorlanmasdan aytish hamda mazkur ertak asosida bayon yozish.
6. O'qituvchi bergan matnni qayta hikoya qilish yoki sahnalashtirish.
7. Insho yozish.

O'quvchilarning bog'lanishli nutqini rivojlantirib borish bilan bir qatorda ularning insho yozish ko'nikmasi ham shakllantirib boriladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini insho yozishga o'rgatishda quyidagi usullaridan foydalanishni tavsiya qilish mumkin.

“Rasmlarni o'qish” mashqi

Bu mashq “Kichik guruhlar bilan ishlash” usulida olib boriladi. O'quvchilar 5-6 kishilik kichik guruhlariga bo'linadi va ularga syujetli rasmlar tarqatiladi. Guruhlar quyidagi bosqichlarda ish olib boradilar:

1-bosqich: Har bir guruh a'zosi rasmda ko'rgan biror tasvirning nomini yozadilar.

2-bosqich: Ushbu so'zni qatnashtirib rasmdagi syujet asosida gap tuzish topshirig'ini bajaradilar.

3-bosqich: O'quvchilarning tuzgan gaplari o'qituvchi yordamida umumlashtiriladi va kichik hikoya tuziladi.

4-bosqich. O'quvchilar tuzgan hikoyalari sarlavha tanlaydilar.

“Gapni to'ldir” mashqi

Ushbu mashqni bajartirishda o'quvchilar ikkitadan juftlikka bo'linadilar. O'qituvchi sodda yig'iq gaplar yozilgan tarqatmalarni juftliklarga berib chiqadi va ushbu tarqatmada berilgan yig'iq gaplarni yoyiq gapga aylantirish, ya'ni uni kengaytirish topshirig'ini beradi.

Namuna: *Bahor keldi. O'lkamizga fasllar kelinchagi -- bahor fasli kirib keldi.*

Ushbu mashq turi o'quvchilarda o'z fikrlarini badiiy tarzda erkin ifodalay olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi.

“Rasmlar ketma-ketligi” mashqi

Bu mashq turi ham “Kichik guruhlar bilan ishlash” usulida olib boriladi. O'quvchilar 5-6 kishilik kichik guruhlariga bo'linadi. Aynan bir mavzu yuzasidan bir necha rasmlar jamlanmasi kichik guruhlariga bittadan tarqatiladi va ularga rasmdagi

tasvir yuzasidan gaplar tuzish topshirig‘i beriladi. Ushbu mashq quyidagi ikki bosqichda olib boriladi.

1-bosqichda o‘quvchilar kichik guruhlarda o‘zlariga berilgan rasm yuzasidan gaplar tuzadilar.

2-bosqichda esa barcha guruh a‘zolari birgalikda o‘qituvchi rahbarligida tuzilgan gaplarni ketma-ketlikda matn holiga keltiradilar. Ushbu mashq o‘quvchilarni asosiy fikrni aniqlash va fikrni umumlashtirishga o‘rgatishda qo‘l keladi.

“Akvarium” mashqi

Bunda sinf o‘quvchilari qo‘llariga qog‘oz va ruchka oladilar va doira shaklida stullarga joylashadilar. Doira markazida beshta a‘lochi o‘quvchi o‘tiradi. O‘tirganlar o‘qituvchi tavsiya qilgan mavzu yuzasidan suhbat uyushtiradilar, qolgan o‘quvchilar esa suhbatni tinglaydilar va uning qisqacha mazmunini yozib olishga harakat qiladilar. Suhbat yakunlanganidan keyin o‘quvchilarga yozib olgan suhbatni inshoga aylantirish topshirig‘i beriladi.

Insho yozish uchun, avvalo, bilim egallash zarur. Takror va takror yozish natijasida esa insho yozish ko‘nikma va malakasi shakllanadi. Yaxshi inshoning zamirida boy bilim va tinimsiz mashq yotadi. [2.] Shunday ekan, boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarida insho yozish ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish ona tili o‘qituvchisidan alohida e‘tibor, shu bilan bir qatorda pedagogik mahorat talab qiladi.

Ona tili o‘qituvchisining insho yozish ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishni izchillik bilan ketma-ketlik tamoyillari asosida olib borishi o‘quvchilarning so‘z boyligi, og‘zaki va yozma nutqining rivojlanishi, mustaqil fikrlash, insho yozish ko‘nikmalarining mustahkamlanib borishi va malakaga aylanishida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PHILOLOGY DIRECTION STUDENTS

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Abstract. This study investigates the effectiveness of the **Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)** method in enhancing English language proficiency among philology students. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the research analyzes quantitative data from pre- and post-intervention assessments and qualitative insights from student and instructor feedback. The findings indicate that the CLT method significantly improves language competence, particularly in speaking and writing skills, and increases student motivation and engagement (AL-Garni & Almuhammadi, 2019; Khowatim, Farid & Saifuddin, 2022).

Key words: *CLT, linguistics, pre-while-post, philology student.*

Аннотация. В этом исследовании изучается эффективность метода коммуникативного обучения языку (CLT) в повышении уровня владения английским языком среди студентов-филологов. Используя подход смешанных методов, исследование анализирует количественные данные оценок до и после вмешательства, а также качественные данные отзывов студентов и преподавателей. Результаты показывают, что метод CLT значительно улучшает языковую компетентность, особенно навыки говорения и письма, и повышает мотивацию и вовлеченность студентов (AL-Garni & Almuhammadi, 2019; Khowatim, Farid & Saifuddin, 2022).

Ключевые слова: CLT, лингвистика, pre-while-post, студент-филолог.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot filologiya talabalari o'rtasida ingliz tilini bilish darajasini oshirishda Kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish (CLT) usulining samaradorligi o'rganildi. Aralash usullardan foydalangan holda, tadqiqotdan oldingi va keyingi baholashning miqdoriy ma'lumotlarini va talabalar fikr-mulohazasidan olingan mavzuga oid tushunchalarni tahlil qilindi. Izlanishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, CLT usuli til kompetensiyasini, ayniqsa nutq va yozish ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi va o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi va faolligini oshiradi (AL-Garni & Almuhammadi, 2019; Khowatim, Farid & Saifuddin, 2022).

Kalit so'zlar: CLT, tilshunoslik, pre-while-post, filologiya talabasi.

Introduction. Philology students engage deeply with the historical, linguistic, and literary aspects of language. For them, learning English is not only about grammar and vocabulary but also about developing communicative competence, cultural awareness, and interpretative skills. Traditional teaching methods, such as the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), often focus on reading and writing accuracy rather than practical language use (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). However, **Communicative Language Teaching**, introduced by linguists such as **Dell Hymes (1972)** and further developed by **Canale and Swain (1980)**, focuses on real-life

communication, fluency, and the functional use of language. This makes it highly relevant to philology students who must interpret texts, express nuanced ideas, and engage in discourse analysis.

This study investigates how CLT, rooted in these theoretical foundations, can effectively address the linguistic needs of philology students.

Methods. Research Design

This study employed a **quasi-experimental design**, comparing a control group taught through traditional methods and an experimental group taught using the CLT method. The objective was to assess the influence of CLT on students' performance in speaking and writing – two essential skills for philology students.

Participants. The study involved **24 undergraduate philology students** from ISFT. 12 students were assigned to the control group, and 12 to the experimental group. Both groups were comparable in gender, academic year, and baseline proficiency levels.

Intervention. The experimental group received instruction through CLT-based activities for 12 weeks. These included:

- **Role-plays and simulations**
- **Information gap and opinion gap activities**
- **Task-based learning**
- **Group discussions and peer interviews**

These activities align with CLT principles advocated by **Littlewood (1981)** and **Savignon (2002)**, emphasizing student interaction and meaningful communication.

The control group received instruction through traditional grammar-focused lessons and translation exercises typical of the GTM.

Data Collection. To measure learning outcomes:

- Pre- and post-tests (standardized speaking and writing assessments) were administered.
- A student motivation questionnaire based on **Gardner's (1985)** Attitude/Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) was used.
- Semi-structured interviews were conducted with instructors and randomly selected students.

Data Analysis. Quantitative data were analyzed using **paired sample t-tests** and **ANCOVA** to determine statistically significant differences.

- Qualitative data were analyzed through **thematic coding** to extract recurring themes on learner engagement and classroom interaction.

Results. Quantitative Results

The experimental group showed a **20% mean improvement** in overall English proficiency, with significant gains in:

- **Speaking skills:** +25% average improvement

- **Writing skills:** +18% average improvement

Compared to the control group (which showed only 5% and 4% gains respectively), the results are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

AL-Garni and Almuhammadi (2019) found similar results with Saudi university students, where CLT increased speaking proficiency and confidence levels. Likewise, **Khowatim, Farid, and Saifuddin (2022)** reported statistically significant improvements in oral production among Asian EFL learners.

Motivation and Engagement. Students in the CLT group showed higher motivation, with 85% reporting that CLT activities were “**interesting and encouraging**”, as opposed to only 42% in the control group. This confirms findings by **Basir, Ampa, and Sulfasyah (2021)**, who emphasized that CLT boosts learners' motivation and reduces classroom anxiety.

Discussion. The study reinforces that **CLT is effective for philology students**, who require not only accuracy but also fluency and cultural literacy. The theoretical foundation laid by **Hymes (1972)** and further elaborated by **Canale and Swain (1980)** provides a robust justification for its application. These scholars argue that communicative competence includes grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competence – all vital for philological analysis and interpretation.

The integration of real-world communication tasks under CLT allowed students to **use English contextually**, mirroring real academic and professional scenarios. According to **Littlewood (1981)**, such activities foster greater learner autonomy, which is critical for advanced language users like philology students.

Moreover, this research aligns with **Sitorus et al. (2023)**, who concluded that CLT is particularly beneficial in developing essay-writing skills among university students.

Conclusion. This study confirms that the **Communicative Language Teaching method significantly enhances English proficiency, motivation, and communicative competence among philology students**. By moving beyond mechanical language practice, CLT nurtures real-world linguistic abilities aligned with the academic and analytical demands of philological studies.

Educators should consider incorporating CLT strategies into English courses for philology students to foster deeper linguistic engagement and better prepare students for academic discourse and cross-cultural communication.

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MODERN TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING LISTENING

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Abstract

Listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This involves understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, his grammar and his vocabulary, and grasping his meaning. An able listener is capable of doing these four things simultaneously. The scholars lists a series of micro-skills of listening, which they call enabling skills.

Key words: pupils, visual, methods, activity

Аннотация.

Умение слушать — это способность распознавать и понимать, что говорят другие. Это подразумевает понимание акцента или произношения говорящего, его грамматики и словарного запаса, а также понимание смысла его речи. Умный слушатель способен делать эти четыре вещи одновременно. Ученые перечисляют ряд микронавыков слушания, которые они называют вспомогательными навыками.

Ключевые слова: ученики, наглядность, методы, деятельность.

Annotatsiya

Tinglash - bu boshqalarning aytganlarini tushunish va tushunish qobiliyati. Bu so'zlovchining urg'usi yoki talaffuzini, grammatika va lug'atini, nutqining ma'nosini tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi. Aqlli tinglovchi bir vaqtning o'zida ushbu to'rtta narsani qila oladi. Olimlar tinglashning bir qancha mikro-ko'nikmalarini sanab o'tadilar, ularni ular pastki ko'nikmalar deb atashadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quvchilar, ko'rgazmali qurollar, usullar, faoliyat.

Effective, modern methods of teaching listening skills encompass everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening skills are best learned through simple, engaging activities that focus more on the learning process than on the final product. Whether you are working with a large group of students or a small one, you can use any of the following examples to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen well.

In our article, we listed the following subdivisions of modern listening techniques. They are kinesthetic, verbal/aural and visual.

Kinesthetic pupils learn best when they move and groove—that is, when they get their bodies involved in the activity. Here are some listening activities you can do that will get students up and moving in class.

Simon Says

Simon Says is a great go-to listening game. It's practically perfect for teaching with Total Physical Response. When your students play Simon Says, they will have to follow simple commands and move their bodies in the way you direct them.

This game is also great for reviewing vocabulary or grammar structures if you make a point of including them in your verbal directions.

Verbal/aural students do best when they hear or speak what you want them to learn. You can try these next activities for students who learn best by listening.

Hearing is Believing

Before listening to a dialogue, play some background noise that matches the location of your scene and have students make predictions about what will be in the dialogue.

For example, play a movie clip (without visual or dialogue) that occurs in a restaurant (like this one) before playing a dialogue of people ordering food.

Back-to-back Interviews

In Back-to-back Interviews, have two students sit back to back to remove the visual clues from their conversation. Give one student a famous person to role play and have the other person ask ten interview questions, noting the answers that their partner gives.

Can the interviewer guess who the interviewee is? After the interview have students switch roles and give the interviewee a different celebrity to role play.

Not Quite Identical

Have students work with a partner to pinpoint differences in nearly identical sentences. To prepare this activity, write up a list of ten sentences: list A. Then rewrite those sentences making slight changes—two or three changes for each sentence such as word choice or verb tense. This is list B.

Give list A to one student and list B to their partner, having the two work together to find the differences. During the activity, students are not permitted to look at one another's papers—so they must speak and listen.

Did You Overhear That?

If you can take your students on a mini field trip, have them sit quietly and listen to sounds at a café, restaurant or other public place. Have students write about what they are hearing—especially if they manage to overhear any conversations.

Visual learners learn through what they see. It's possible to have listening activities tailored for visual learners—try some of the following.

Movie Vocabulary

Have students listen for specific vocabulary in a favorite movie clip. Before class choose a movie clip and prewatch it, noting any interesting or unusual vocabulary. Type up the words in list form. Keep them in order for an easier listening activity and randomize them for a more challenging activity. In class give your students copies of the vocabulary list. Review the pronunciation with students and then play the movie clip for them. Have students mark off the words as they hear them. After watching the clip, see who heard the most words and discuss the meaning of any words your students don't already know.

Sound Vocabulary

If you are doing a vocabulary unit on animals, modes of transportation or anything else that leads itself to specific noises, try having your students match sounds to words. Give them vocabulary words on index cards or in a numbered list.

Play sounds associated with each word, such as sounds that the item makes, sounds you might hear at that place, or conversations that might happen in association with the words. Then have students match each sound clip to the appropriate vocabulary word.

Conclusion

We have outlined the main reasons for teaching listening comprehension in a foreign language. It is now widely accepted that oral communication plays a vital role in second language teaching for it provides an exposure to language which is a fundamental requirement for the learner. Progress in listening guarantees a basis for development of other language skills. The lesson theme should be presented in the form of the text, game, and various pictures or with the help of video lessons. The aim of

listening activities is to achieve students' desire to learn to listen to speech and understand the hearing, and to make them feel their capabilities, their progress. Listening is the basis of communication; it begins with the mastery of oral communication.

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Вопросы преподавания узбекского языка в неязыковых группах высших учебных заведений

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mamlakat oliy o'quv yurtlarida rus tilida so'zlashuvchilarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi, o'qituvchilar va talabalar duch keladigan qiyinchiliklar, ikki tilning tovush va harflaridagi farqlar bayon qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat tili, rusiyzabonlik, dolzarblik, salohiyat, talaffuz, muloqot imkoniyatlari.

Abstract: This article examines the teaching of Uzbek to native Russian speakers in the country's universities, describes the difficulties faced by teachers and students, and the differences in the sounds and letters of the two languages.

Keywords: state language, Russian-speaking, relevance, difference, communication opportunities.

Аннотация: В настоящей статье рассмотрено обучение носителей русского языка узбекскому языку в вузах страны, описаны трудности, с которыми сталкиваются преподаватели и студенты, различия звуков и букв двух языков.

Ключевые слова: государственный язык, русскоязычные, актуальность, потенциал, различие, произношение, коммуникативные возможности.

Около 85% населения Узбекистана составляют этнические узбеки, которые говорят на государственном языке. Однако среди русскоязычных узбекистанцев все еще остается актуальной проблема незнания узбекского языка. Конечно, радует, что при таких условиях постепенно увеличивается количество наших иностранных друзей, полюбивших узбекский язык и знающих его с нами наравне, кроме того, необходимо превратить изучение

государственного языка в жизненную необходимость. Поскольку дать правильное направление желающим изучать узбекский язык, пробудить в них любовь и интерес к нашему языку – это значит пробудить интерес к нашей истории, культуре, искусству, потенциалу в сфере национального туризма, и в целом, ко всему Узбекистану.

Обучение студентов неязыковых факультетов узбекскому языку также на сегодняшний день приобретает особое значение. Ни для кого не секрет, что преподавание узбекского языка в учебных заведениях по различным объективным и субъективным причинам ведется не на должном научно-методическом уровне и предпочтение отдается по сей день традиционным методам обучения, хотя программа и учебники в общеобразовательных школах составлены с учётом коммуникативных возможностей обучающихся. Мы это должны обязательно учитывать.

На наш взгляд, курс узбекского языка как неродного должен обеспечить знание языковых норм произношения, постановку ударений, словообразование, умение верно использовать выразительные средства языка в различных формах и условиях общения.

Задача преподавателя узбекского языка в группах неязыковых факультетов вузов заключается в том, чтобы научить студентов выражать свои мысли в устной и письменной форме с использованием языковых и речевых средств узбекского языка. Мы должны учитывать и то, что наш курс - это практический курс, развивающий речевые навыки и умения студентов. И поэтому этот курс должен быть построен с учётом коммуникативной направленности обучения языку. Для этого нам в первую очередь необходимо перейти от традиционной грамматики предложения к функционально-коммуникативной грамматике целого текста, разъяснению функции языковых средств, выработке на этой основе определённых речевых умений и навыков: аудирование, продуцирование устной и письменной речи.

Как показывает практика, одним из основных препятствий при обучении узбекскому языку студентов является различный уровень их речевой и языковой подготовленности. Обучающиеся, только приступающие самостоятельно к изучению узбекского языка должны помнить следующее:

а) Не усвоив прочно весь материал первого урока или/и всех предыдущих уроков, никогда не надо начинать изучать следующий.

б) Всё усвоенное (слова, формы слов, сочетания слов, предложения) нужно стараться использовать при диалогах, не боясь допустить ошибки, так как никто и никогда не сможет сразу научиться абсолютно правильно говорить на изучаемом языке, нужно просить своих сокурсников, товарищей, друзей и знакомых, хорошо владеющих узбекским языком (узбеков, носителей языка),

чтобы они указывали на Ваши типичные ошибки в произношении (при разговоре) на узбекском языке и при чтении текстов на узбекском языке, а также на характерные грамматические ошибки. И далее в своей речи надо по возможности учитывать эти указания и поправки. В идеале, конечно, нужно стараться подражать произношению людей, в совершенстве владеющих узбекским литературным языком.

в) Иногда, если нет времени, то можно не обращать внимание на некоторые несложные грамматические и прочие объяснения и примечания, которые даются во время занятий. Лучше лишний раз перечитать вслух узбекские фразы с участием этих грамматических конструкций (с переводом их на русский язык) и диалоги, постараться их запомнить.

г) При выполнении некоторых несложных упражнений элементарного уровня необходимо помнить, что эти упражнения можно выполнять только устно и притом обязательно вслух. А ещё лучше было бы выполнять эти упражнения устно под контролем товарища или узбекоговорящего члена семьи, который следил бы за правильностью выполнения этих упражнений. Надо стараться как можно больше читать и перечитывать знакомые фразы и тексты и, конечно, как можно больше говорить по-узбекски при всяком удобном случае.

д) Нужно помнить, что практическое владение узбекской речью предполагает не только умение выразить своя мысли на узбекском языке, но еще и умение со слуха понимать собеседников, говорящих с Вами по-узбекски (ведь собеседники в повседневной жизни, во-первых, всегда говорят медленно и разборчиво и, во-вторых совершенно не соблюдают правил книжного произношения и произносят узбекские слова и фразы так, как их обычно произносят все люди, свободно и бегло говорящие). Если Вы будете произносить узбекские слова, формы слов и предложения, придерживаясь правил литературного произношения, то Вас прекрасно поймут, но когда Вам будут отвечать по-узбекски или задавать вопросы на узбекском языке, то далеко не всегда и не все будут строго соблюдать правила узбекского литературного произношения, и Вы можете не понять из-за этого даже самые простые фразы.

ж) Надо всё время стараться расширять свой запас узбекских слов и выражений. Если будут прочно усвоены практически основные типы предложений, формы слов и типы сочетаний слов, то усваивая на практике всё новые и новые слова, сочетания слов и синтаксические обороты, в течение нескольких месяцев (после усвоения всего необходимого материала) вполне возможно практически овладеть узбекским языком настолько, чтобы общаться на нём с людьми, владеющими узбекской речью.

з) При всякой возможности надо внимательно слушать живую узбекскую речь (выступления ораторов на собраниях, радио и телепередачи, спектакли и

постановки в узбекских театрах, кинофильмы, озвученные на узбекском языке и т. д. и т.п)

Общие указания и предварительные задания при изучении узбекского языка.

1. Звуки и буквы в узбекском языке похожи и не совсем похожи на звуки русского языка. Большие различия существуют между гласными звуками этих языков. Таким образом, хотя при написании большинства узбекских гласных звуков буквами кириллицы применяются буквы русского алфавита (*а, э, и, о, у и др.*), надо всегда помнить, что эти буквы обозначают в русском языке одни звуки, а в узбекском языке другие звуки (правда в той или иной степени похожие на соответствующие русские звуки). Есть только один узбекский гласный звук, обозначаемый особой буквой, - это звук *у* (средний между русскими звуками «*о*» и «*у*»). Вместе с тем в узбекском алфавите нет буквы «*ы*», так как в узбекском языке не имеется самостоятельного гласного звука, подобного русскому звуку «*ы*» (некоторые оттенки узбекского гласного звука *и*, похожие на русский звук «*ы*», обозначаются буквой *и*, и это не вызывает никаких трудностей при чтении узбекского текста человеком, который хорошо владеет узбекским языком).

2. Что же касается согласных звуков узбекского языка, то многие из них очень сходны по своему произношению с соответствующими согласными русского языка и обозначаются теми же самыми буквами, что и русские согласные. Так, например, следующие 11 согласных звуков в обоих языках произносятся почти одинаково

Вместе с тем в узбекском языке нет согласного звука «*щ*», и в алфавите нет буквы «*щ*». Зато есть особые согласные звуки *қ, ғ и х*, которых нет в русском языке и которые поэтому обозначаются особыми буквами.

Далее, произношение некоторых узбекских согласных звуков, например звуков, обозначаемых буквами *в, г, ж, к, л, х, ш*, существенно отличается от произношения русских согласных, обозначаемых этими же буквами.

Объяснять произношение таких узбекских согласных звуков, как *б, д, м* и др. не обязательно, так как усвоить их произношение человеку, владеющему русским языком, очень легко. Однако это не означает, что так же легко будет овладеть произношением сочетаний указанных узбекских согласных звуков с гласными звуками.

Возьмём один-два примера. Так, сочетания узбекских согласных звуков *д, т, н* с узбекскими гласными *и, е* (т. е. сочетания, обозначаемые буквами *ди, де, ти, те, ни, не*) произносятся совсем не так, как русские сочетания звуков, которые обозначаются этими же буквами. В узбекских сочетаниях звуков *ди, де, ти, те, ни, не* согласные звуки *д, т, н* почти не смягчаются, а в соответствующих русских сочетаниях русские согласные «*д*», «*т*» и «*н*», на-оборот, очень сильно

смягчаются (кроме того, узбекские гласные звуки в этих сочетаниях, обозначаемые буквами *и* и *е*, тоже произносятся не так, как русские гласные, которые обозначаются теми же буквами в соответствующих русских сочетаниях звуков). Далее, хотя в узбекских сочетаниях звуков *зи*, *зе*, *ри*, *ре*, *си*, *се* согласные звуки *з*, *р* и *с* немного смягчаются, но не так сильно, как русские согласные «з», «р» и «с» смягчаются в русских сочетаниях «зи», «зе», «ри», «ре», «си», «се». Кроме того, надо помнить, что гласные звуки *и*, *е* в узбекских сочетаниях *зи*, *зе*, *ри*, *ре*, *си*, *се* произносятся не так, как русские гласные «и» и «е» в русских сочетаниях «зи», «зе», «ри», «ре», «си», «се».

Звуки узбекского языка надо учиться произносить в словах и предложениях, потому что в естественной, живой речи изолированные, т. е. одиночные, звуки почти никогда не произносятся.

Самое оптимальное и действенное решение — это ежедневно заниматься узбекским языком по интернету, самоучителю или учебнику 1-2 часа (желательно при консультации и под контролем лица, хорошо владеющего практически узбекской речью). Но если времени нет, то можно заниматься и по 30-40 минут в день, но обязательно регулярно.

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Инновации в обучении дошкольников иностранному языку.

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga chet tillarini o'rgatish usullari va innovatsiyalariga e'tibor qaratilgan va materialni osonroq va tezroq o'zlashtirish uchun jarayonni qanday tashkil qilish kerakligi haqida savol berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiya, maktabgacha tarbiyachi, texnologiya, ekologiya, integratsiya.

Abstract. The article focuses on methods and innovations in the issue of teaching foreign languages to preschoolers, reveals the question of how to organize the process so that the material is learned easier and faster.

Keywords: innovation, preschooler, technology, ecology, integration.

Аннотация. В статье уделяется внимание методам и инновациям в вопросе обучения иностранным языкам дошкольников, раскрывается вопрос о том, каким образом организовать процесс для того, чтобы материал усваивался легче и быстрее.

Ключевые слова: инновация, дошкольник, технологии, экология, интеграция.

В современном обществе образование выдвигается в число ведущих областей деятельности общества, входит в круг факторов, определяющих будущее страны. Это обусловлено тем, что система образования является основой экономического и социального развития страны. Для развития и процветания нашего государства необходимо формирование интеллектуального потенциала нации, поскольку Узбекистану, вступающему в мировое образовательное сообщество, предстоит стать конкурентоспособным государством.

Всем известно, как велико значение дошкольного детства в формировании личности ребенка. Наверное, трудно найти человека, который не понимал бы: в детских садах, действительно, все должно быть самым лучшим — игрушки, продукты питания, помещения и прежде всего — люди, постоянно находящиеся рядом с малышами. Сегодня подготовка дошкольников к системе образования немислима без использования в процессе обучения последних достижений. Инновационные технологии служат прогрессу нашей страны и повышению интеллектуального потенциала, ибо это требование времени. «Ведущей целью раннего обучения иностранным языкам является, прежде всего, развивающая цель. Обучение иностранным языкам детей-дошкольников призвано содействовать охране и укреплению физического и психического здоровья детей, развитию их индивидуальных способностей»⁵⁵.

В деле достижения этой цели первейшей задачей становится необходимость широкого внедрения современных информационных систем и технологий в систему непрерывного образования. Определение «инновация» как педагогический критерий встречается часто и сводится, как правило, к понятию «новшество», «новизна». Между тем, инновация в точном переводе с латинского языка обозначает не «новое», а «в новое». Именно эту смысловую нагрузку вложил в термин «инновационное» в конце прошлого века Дж. Боткин. Он и наметил основные черты «дидактического портрета» этого метода,

⁵⁵ Опубликовано 27.09.2019 - 18:09 - Николаева Вера Александровна
<https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannye-yazyki/angliiskiy-yazyk/library/2019/09/27/rannee-obuchenie-inostrannomu-yazyku>

направленного на развитие способности обучаемого к самосовершенствованию, самостоятельному поиску решений, к совместной деятельности в новой ситуации. Инновационные технологии обучения следует рассматривать как инструмент, с помощью которого новая образовательная парадигма может быть претворена в жизнь.⁵⁶

Каковы же критерии инновационности учебных заведений? Инновации в дошкольном образовании, изучение иностранных языков в детском саду играют важную роль в развитии детей и подготовке их к школе. Вот несколько ключевых направлений и подходов, которые активно внедряются в эту сферу:

Игровые технологии: Использование игровых методов обучения, помогает детям развивать социальные навыки, креативность и критическое мышление. Игровые технологии для дошкольников при изучении языка могут включать разнообразные методы и подходы, которые делают процесс обучения увлекательным и эффективным. Вот несколько идей:

1. Ролевые игры: дети могут разыгрывать различные сценарии, такие как «Магазин», «Ресторан» или семейные ситуации. Это помогает им практиковать новый словарный запас и фразы в контексте. **Игры на запоминание:** использование карточек с изображениями и словами. Дети могут играть в игры, такие как "Пары" или "Мемори", чтобы запомнить новые слова. **Музыкальные игры:** песни и рифмовки помогают детям запоминать слова и фразы. Использование музыкальных инструментов и танцев для создания более интерактивной среды. **Драматизация:** можно попросить детей инсценировать сказки или истории. Это не только развивает языковые навыки, но и творческое мышление.

2. Настольные игры: создайте или используйте существующие настольные игры, которые требуют использования языка, например, "Словесные домино" или "Словесные лото".

3. Картинки и визуальные материалы: использование ярких картинок, плакатов и книг с иллюстрациями для обсуждения и описания объектов, действий и эмоций.

4. Игры с движением: игры, требующие физических действий, такие как "Simon Says" или "Follow the Leader", могут быть адаптированы для практики языка, где команды даются на изучаемом языке.

5. Кулинарные мастер-классы: готовка простых блюд может включать изучение новых слов и фраз, связанных с едой и процессом приготовления.

⁵⁶ Дербердеева Т.Х. Новые ценности в образовании в условиях информационного общества/ Т.Х. Дербердеева// Инновации в образовании. - 2005.-№3.-с.79

6. Творческие проекты: создание поделок, рисунков или других творческих работ с последующей презентацией результатов на изучаемом языке.

По утверждению одного из современных разработчиков этой технологии обучения Е.С. Полат, «метод проектов – суть развивающего, личностно ориентированного обучения. Он может использоваться на любой ступени обучения, в том числе и в средней школе»⁵⁷.

Эти технологии помогают детям развивать языковые навыки в комфортной и увлекательной обстановке, что способствует более глубокому усвоению материала.

Интеграция STEM-образования (наука, технологии, инженерия и математика) для дошкольников — это важный шаг в развитии детей, который помогает формировать у них критическое мышление, креативность и навыки решения проблем. Вот несколько подходов и идей для внедрения STEM-образования в дошкольные учреждения:

1. Научные эксперименты: Простые эксперименты, такие как смешивание воды и краски или наблюдение за растущими растениями, могут вызвать интерес к науке.

2. Тематические проекты. Проекты по исследованию окружающего мира на изучаемом языке: например, изучение различных экосистем (лес, море, пустыня) через игры и практические занятия.

3. Интеграция с искусством. STEAM-подход: включение искусства в STEM-образование (STEAM) помогает детям развивать креативное мышление. Например, создание моделей или рисунков, связанных с научными темами проведение занятий по рисованию, лепке и другим видам искусства на иностранном языке.

4. Использование технологий. Образовательные приложения: Использование планшетов и компьютеров с образовательными приложениями, которые обучают иностранным языкам в игровой форме. Виртуальные экскурсии: Проведение виртуальных экскурсий в музеи, выставки и другие образовательные учреждения.

5. Сотрудничество с родителями. Вовлечение родителей в процесс изучения языков: организация мероприятий, где родители могут участвовать в STEM-активностях вместе с детьми, что способствует укреплению связи между домом и образовательным учреждением.

7. Создание STEM-уголков, уголки для экспериментов: обустройство специальных зон в классе, с надписями на разных языках, где дети могут самостоятельно проводить эксперименты и исследовать различные материалы.

⁵⁷ Полат Е.С. Метод проектов на уроках иностранного языка/Иностранные языки в школе// №2,3 . - 2000.- С53.

Интеграция STEM-образования для дошкольников требует творческого подхода и использования разнообразных методов обучения языкам. Важно, чтобы обучение проходило в игровой и увлекательной форме, что поможет детям развивать интерес к науке и технологиям с раннего возраста.

Экологическое воспитание: использование программ по экологическому образованию, которые учат детей заботиться о природе и осознавать важность устойчивого развития. Экологическое воспитание для дошкольников — это эффективный подход, который позволяет развивать у детей интерес к науке, технологиям, инженерии и математике, а также формировать экологическую грамотность. Вот несколько идей и методов, как это можно реализовать:

1. Тематические проекты, экологические исследования: дети могут проводить простые эксперименты, например, изучать, как растения растут в разных условиях (свет, вода, почва). Сбор и анализ данных: Использование простых таблиц для записи наблюдений о погоде, росте растений или количестве насекомых на участке.

2. Игровые активности, строительство экосистемы: создание мини-экосистемы в классе (например, террариум или аквариум) и изучение его компонентов. Ролевые игры: Дети могут разыгрывать роли животных или растений на иностранном языке, чтобы понять их место в экосистеме.

3. Языковая интеграция, использование многоязычных материалов: книги, игры и видео на разных языках, связанные с экологией и STEM. Обсуждение экологических тем, введение новых слов и понятий на изучаемом языке через экологические темы: например, названия растений, животных, природных явлений.

4. Внешние исследования, экскурсии на природу: походы в парки или заповедники, где дети могут наблюдать за природой и собирать образцы, обсуждая новые слова и понятия (листья, камни и т.д.). Садоводство: создание и уход за садом, где дети могут учить о растениях и экосистемах на практике.

5. Технологические инструменты, использование приложений и игр: мобильные приложения, которые обучают детей основам экологии на иностранном языке через интерактивные игры. Создание мультимедийных проектов: дети могут создавать презентации или короткие видео на изучаемом языке о своих наблюдениях и исследованиях.

6. Обсуждение актуальных тем: обсуждение простых концепций, таких как переработка сырья, мусора, сохранение воды и энергии.

7. Социальные проекты: участие в акциях по очистке территории или посадке деревьев, что поможет детям понять важность заботы о природе.

Интеграция STEM-образования и экологического воспитания в дошкольном возрасте способствует не только развитию речи, мышления, но и

формированию ответственного и бережного отношения к окружающему миру. Это помогает детям развивать навыки, которые будут полезны в будущем, а также учит их важности сохранения природы.

Эти инновации помогают создать более динамичную и адаптивную образовательную среду для детей дошкольного возраста, способствуя их всестороннему развитию.

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TILLAR VA RAQAMLI MAKON

LANGUAGES AND THE DIGITAL SPACE

ЯЗЫКИ И ЦИФРОВОЕ ПРОСТРАНСТВО

Politeness in Social Media Discourse

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Abstract

In the contemporary era dominated by digital interaction, social media has emerged as a primary medium for interpersonal exchange. This dissertation investigates the articulation of politeness within social media discourse, analyzing the extent to which users recalibrate conventional politeness strategies in response to the structural affordances and communicative constraints of digital platforms. Anchored in Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory and enriched by frameworks concerning face negotiation, this research scrutinizes both linguistic and paralinguistic elements employed to enact politeness in the absence of traditional non-verbal cues. Utilizing a qualitative, discourse-analytical methodology, the study foregrounds the function of emojis, textual stylization, hedging devices, and indirect formulations in facilitating both positive and negative politeness. Examples sourced from Twitter, Reddit, Instagram, and Facebook elucidate how politeness is pragmatically enacted in various online contexts. The findings underscore the adaptability of politeness strategies and their embeddedness within platform-specific norms and cultural discourses.

Key words: Politeness strategies, social media discourse, computer-mediated communication (CMC), face theory, intercultural pragmatics, paralinguistic features, emojis, discourse analysis, online interaction, digital communication norms.

Аннотация

В современную эпоху, характеризующуюся цифровым взаимодействием, социальные сети стали основным средством межличностного общения. Настоящее исследование рассматривает реализацию вежливости в узбекском дискурсе социальных сетей, анализируя, в какой степени пользователи адаптируют традиционные стратегии вежливости в соответствии со структурными возможностями и коммуникативными ограничениями цифровых платформ. Основываясь на теории вежливости Брауна и Левинсона и обогащённая концепциями «сохранения лица», работа исследует как лингвистические, так и паралингвистические средства, используемые для выражения вежливости в условиях отсутствия традиционных невербальных сигналов. Применяя качественную дискурсивно-аналитическую методологию, исследование фокусируется на функциях эмодзи, текстовой стилизации, смягчающих выражений и косвенных формулировок в реализации позитивной и негативной вежливости. Примеры, взятые с таких платформ, как Telegram, Facebook и Instagram, демонстрируют прагматическое воплощение вежливости в различных узбекских онлайн-контекстах. Полученные результаты подчёркивают адаптивность стратегий вежливости и их укоренённость в платформенно-специфичных нормах и социокультурных дискурсах.

Ключевые слова: Стратегии вежливости, дискурс в социальных сетях, компьютерно-опосредованная коммуникация (КОК), теория «лица», межкультурная прагматика, паралингвистические особенности, эмодзи, дискурсивный анализ, онлайн-взаимодействие,

нормы цифровой коммуникации.

Annotatsiya

Raqamli muloqot hukmronlik qilayotgan hozirgi davrda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar shaxslararo munosabatlarning asosiy vositasiga aylangan. Ushbu tadqiqot ijtimoiy media diskursida xushmuomalalikning ifodalanishini o'rganadi va foydalanuvchilar raqamli platformalarning strukturaviy imkoniyatlari va kommunikativ cheklovlariga javoban an'anaviy xushmuomalalik strategiyalarini qay darajada moslashtirishini tahlil qiladi. Brown va Levinsonning xushmuomalalik nazariyasiga tayangan holda, "yuzi saqlanishi"ga oid yondashuvlar bilan boyitilgan ushbu izlanish lingvistik va paralingvistik vositalarning, ya'ni emodzildan, matn uslublaridan, yumshatuvchi ifodalar va bilvosita so'zlashuv shakllaridan foydalanish orqali xushmuomalalikni qanday amalga oshirishini o'rganadi. Sifatli nutq tahliliga asoslangan metodologiya yordamida olib borilgan tadqiqotda Telegram, Facebook va Instagram kabi platformalardan olingan misollar asosida xushmuomalalikning o'zbek onlayn kontekstlarida qanday aks etishi ko'rsatib beriladi. Natijalar xushmuomalalik strategiyalarining moslashuvchanligini va ularning platformaga xos normalar hamda madaniy diskurslarga qanday chuqur singib ketganligini namoyon qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xushmuomalalik strategiyalari, ijtimoiy media diskursi, kompyuter vositasida amalga oshiriladigan kommunikatsiya (CMC), yuz nazariyasi, madaniyatlararo pragmatika, paralingvistik xususiyatlar, emodzilar, diskurs tahlili, onlayn muloqot, raqamli kommunikatsiya normalari.

Introduction

The advent of social media has engendered a profound transformation in human communication, reconfiguring the modalities through which individuals connect across sociocultural and geographical boundaries. Digital platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok afford asynchronous, multimodal engagement that subverts traditional interactional paradigms. Among the communicative aspects most significantly affected is the phenomenon of politeness, which functions as a cornerstone of interpersonal harmony and relational management. In contrast to face-to-face interaction, digital discourse is deprived of prosodic features, facial expressions, and gestures—cues which are integral to encoding and decoding politeness. Consequently, users are compelled to innovate alternative mechanisms to express deference, affiliation, and courtesy within a disembodied textual environment.

Literature Review

The corpus of existing scholarship attests to the intricate nature of politeness within computer-mediated communication (CMC). Central to this body of work is Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory, which delineates politeness into positive strategies (aimed at reinforcing social bonds) and negative strategies (intended to mitigate imposition). While these constructs have proven robust in analyzing offline interaction, their applicability requires reassessment in the realm of CMC, where the absence of immediate feedback and embodied co-presence necessitates modified communicative behaviors. Empirical studies demonstrate that users frequently mobilize non-verbal surrogates such as emojis, emphatic punctuation, orthographic

stylization, and discourse softeners like "just" and "maybe" to subtly convey politeness. Locher and Graham (2010), in particular, highlight the dialogic nature of relational work online, emphasizing how digital interlocutors navigate face needs through ongoing textual negotiation.

Theoretical Framework

This inquiry is principally grounded in Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory, augmented by Goffman's conceptualization of face and the intercultural discourse approach advanced by Scollon and Scollon. These theoretical lenses afford a nuanced understanding of how communicators endeavor to manage self-image and engage in facework within digital ecosystems marked by anonymity and reduced social presence. Furthermore, the study draws on Herring's (2010) framework for computer-mediated discourse analysis, which categorizes communicative modes along dimensions such as synchronicity, interactivity, and audience reach—all of which mediate the deployment of politeness strategies.

Methodology

Adopting a qualitative research design, the study employs discourse analysis to examine manifestations of politeness in authentic social media interactions. Data is curated from publicly accessible threads and posts on platforms such as Twitter, Reddit, and Instagram. The selection criteria emphasize the presence of politeness indicators, including hedges (e.g., "I believe," "perhaps"), tag questions (e.g., "isn't it?"), emotive emojis (e.g., 😊, 🙏), and indirect speech acts (e.g., "Would you mind if...?" as a mitigation strategy). Illustrative examples include tweets that tactfully challenge opinions (e.g., "I understand your point, though I might add...") and Reddit exchanges that employ humor and self-deprecation to diffuse potential tension.

Analysis and Discussion

The analysis reveals that participants in social media discourse exhibit considerable rhetorical ingenuity in signaling politeness despite the absence of prosodic and gestural cues. Emojis serve not merely as decorative symbols but as pragmatic tools to modulate tone and intent, transforming potentially contentious statements into affiliative overtures. For instance, a blunt assertion such as "That's incorrect" may be rendered less confrontational through the addition of a smiling emoji, thereby performing a face-saving function.

Orthographic practices—including exaggerated punctuation (e.g., "Thanks soooo much!!!") and strategic use of ellipses—function to temper assertiveness and project humility or hesitation. Platform-specific conventions further modulate politeness: on Twitter, brevity compels the use of condensed politeness markers (e.g., "imo" for "in my opinion"), whereas on LinkedIn, discourse is characteristically formal and deferential. Instagram, by contrast, promotes affective expression through visual reinforcement, where emojis and affirmations (e.g., "Stunning! ✨👏") function to

uphold community norms of positivity and support.

The influence of cultural scripts is pronounced. Japanese digital communication tends to prioritize indirectness and hierarchical politeness markers, whereas American users often favor directness tempered by informal politeness cues. Such disparities underscore the potential for pragmatic misalignment in cross-cultural online interaction, wherein expressions intended as polite may be construed as brusque or disingenuous.

Conclusion

The exploration of politeness in social media discourse unveils a complex interplay between traditional communicative norms and the evolving exigencies of digital interaction. While classical politeness frameworks retain explanatory value, their integration with models attuned to multimodality and intercultural variation is essential. The proliferation of textual and visual paralinguistic devices—emojis, punctuation, hedging, and indirect speech—illustrates the adaptive strategies users employ to preserve relational harmony in text-based environments. This analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of contemporary linguistic behavior and offers valuable insights for fostering civility and empathy in virtual communities.

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SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA GEOSIYOSIY RAQOBAT: YANGI DAVRNING XALQARO MUNOSABATLARIDAGI O'ZGARISHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada sun'iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalarining geosiyosiy raqobatdagi o'rni va uning xalqaro munosabatlar tizimiga ta'siri tahlil etiladi. Sun'iy intellektning iqtisodiy, siyosiy va xavfsizlik sohalaridagi imkoniyatlari, shuningdek, yangi davrda davlatlar o'rtasidagi strategik munosabatlarga bo'lgan ta'siri o'rganiladi. Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi geosiyosiy kuchlarning qayta taqsimlanishiga sabab bo'lishi, shu bilan birga, xalqaro munosabatlarda yangi paradigmalarning paydo bo'lishini keltirib chiqarmoqda. Maqolada sun'iy intellektning yangi geosiyosiy dinamikaga qo'shgan hissasi, davlatlarning global siyosatda o'z o'rinlarini mustahkamlash uchun qanday yangi strategiyalar ishlab chiqayotgani yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, geosiyosiy raqobat, xalqaro munosabatlar, global xavfsizlik, raqamli iqtisodiyot, texnologik diplomatiya, sun'iy intellekt xavfsizligi.

Abstract: This article analyzes the role of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in geopolitical competition and their impact on international relations. The study explores the possibilities of AI in economic, political, and security fields, as well as its influence on the strategic relations between countries in the new era. The development of AI technologies is leading to a redistribution of global power dynamics, as well as the emergence of new paradigms in international relations. The article also discusses how AI is shaping the foreign policy and security strategies of leading global powers and its impact on global security.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, geopolitical competition, international relations, global security, digital economy, technological diplomacy, AI security.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется роль технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в геополитической конкуренции и их влияние на международные отношения. Рассматриваются возможности ИИ в экономической, политической и безопасности, а также его влияние на стратегические отношения между странами в новой эпохе. Развитие технологий ИИ приводит к перераспределению глобальной власти, а также появлению новых парадигм в международных отношениях. В статье также рассматривается, как ИИ формирует внешнюю политику и стратегии безопасности ведущих мировых держав и его влияние на глобальную безопасность.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, геополитическая конкуренция, международные отношения, глобальная безопасность, цифровая экономика, технологическая дипломатия, безопасность ИИ.

Kirish

XXI asrda texnologik inqiloblarning asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lgan sun'iy intellekt (AI) global raqobatda yangi o'lchovlarni yaratmoqda. Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi nafaqat iqtisodiy sohalarda, balki siyosat va xavfsizlikda ham katta o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'lmoqda. Xalqaro munosabatlarda sun'iy intellektning ta'siri kundan-kunga ortib bormoqda, chunki u davlatlar o'rtasidagi strategik raqobatni shakllantirishda va yangi diplomatik metodlarni ishlab chiqishda muhim rol o'ynayapti. (Brynjolfsson, E., McAfee, A., 2014). Bu maqolada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining geosiyosiy raqobatdagi roli, ularning global xavfsizlik va diplomatiyaga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Sun'iy intellektning geosiyosiy munosabatlar tizimiga qo'shgan hissasi juda katta. Shu bois, mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi yangi diplomatik yondashuvlar, xavfsizlik choralariidagi yangiliklar, va raqamli iqtisodiyotdagi yangiliklarni tushunish bugungi kunda ahamiyatga ega. Tashqi siyosatdagi va diplomatiyadagi texnologik o'zgarishlarni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish zarur. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi global xavfsizlik, axborot yutug'i va davlatlarning global iqtisodiy o'rinlarini belgilashda qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini chuqurroq tahlil qilish muhimdir. Bu boradagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar va strategik yondashuvlar sun'iy intellektning xalqaro munosabatlar tizimiga qanday ta'sir qilayotgani haqida yaxshiroq tasavvur yaratishga yordam beradi.

Sun'iy intellektning rivojlanishi davlatlarning global siyosatdagi o'rini aniqlashda muhim omilga aylangan. Yirik davlatlar, xususan, AQSh, Xitoy va Rossiya, sun'iy intellektni harbiy texnologiyalarga, iqtisodiy ishlab chiqarishga va axborot strategiyalariga integratsiyalash orqali o'z strategik ustunliklarini oshirishga intilmoqda. (Kissinger, H., 2018). Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining kiritilishi mamlakatlarning siyosiy manevrlari, diplomatik qarorlar va iqtisodiy rivojlanish sohalariidagi raqobatni yangi bosqichga olib chiqmoqda. Misol uchun, Xitoy va AQSh o'rtasidagi raqobat sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari sohasida yangi muvozanatlarni yaratmoqda. Xitoyning "Made in China 2025" strategiyasi, uning texnologik sohadagi o'sishiga, ayniqsa, sun'iy intellekt va kiberxavfsizlik kabi sohalarda yuqori natijalar ko'rsatishga intilishiga asoslangan. AQSh esa sun'iy intellekt sohasida o'zining yetakchiligini saqlab qolish uchun texnologik yutuqlarni rivojlantirishga davom etmoqda. (Brynjolfsson, E., McAfee, A., 2014). Bu ikki davlat o'rtasidagi raqobat geosiyosiy raqobatning yangi shakllarini keltirib chiqarmoqda. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining harbiy sohadagi qo'llanilishi, masalan, avtonom qurollar va robotlar, harbiy kuchlarni yangi o'lchovlarga olib chiqmoqda. Rossiya va AQSh o'rtasida bu borada raqobat kuchaymoqda va yangi harbiy texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish bo'yicha strategiyalar ishlab chiqilmoqda. (Mikhaylov, A., 2020). Shu tarzda, sun'iy intellektning harbiy sohadagi roli xavfsizlik muammolarini yangi darajaga ko'taradi, bu esa global xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan yangi siyosatlarni talab qiladi.

Sun'iy intellektning xavfsizlikka ta'siri jahon miqyosida yangi xavf-xatarlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Harbiy sohada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari avtonom qurollar va robotlashtirilgan tizimlarning rivojlanishiga olib kelmoqda, bu esa global xavfsizlikni yangi tahdidlarga duchor qiladi. (Mikhaylov, A., 2020). Xususan, kiberxavfsizlik va axborot manipulyatsiyasi kabi sohalarda sun'iy intellektning roli yanada kuchaymoqda. Sun'iy intellekt yordamida mamlakatlar o'rtasida kiber urushlar va axborot urushlari olib borilayotganini kuzatish mumkin. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellektning maxfiy ma'lumotlarni aniqlash va raqiblarning raqamli tizimlariga kirib borish imkoniyatlari mavjud. Sun'iy intellektni xavfsizlikka ta'sirini tahlil qilishda, davlatlarning yangi kiberxavfsizlik siyosatlarini ishlab chiqishi zarur. O'zaro kiberhujumlar va axborot manipulyatsiyalarini oldini olish uchun xalqaro hamkorlik va yangi normativ asoslarni ishlab chiqish muhimdir. Shu bilan birga, davlatlar o'rtasida kiberxavfsizlik sohasidagi yangi diplomatik aloqalar va kelishuvlarni shakllantirish zarur.

Sun'iy intellektning diplomatik aloqalarda qo'llanilishi ham yangi geosiyosiy strategiyalarni shakllantiradi. sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari davlatlarga yanada samarali diplomatik qarorlar qabul qilish, xalqaro munosabatlarda o'z o'rinlarini mustahkamlash uchun zarur bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni to'plash imkonini beradi. (Taddeo, M., Floridi, L., 2018). Shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt yordamida xalqaro muammolarni hal qilishda yangi diplomatik strategiyalar, masalan, "raqamli diplomatiya"ni joriy etish mumkin. Bu texnologiyalar orqali davlatlar o'zlarining siyosiy manfaatlarini ilgari surish va yangi ittifoqlar tuzish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Sun'iy intellektning xalqaro munosabatlarga ta'sirini kuchaytirish uchun, davlatlar o'rtasida yangi diplomatik aloqalar va strategiyalarni shakllantirish zarur. sun'iy intellekt yordamida davlatlar o'zlarining diplomatik va iqtisodiy manfaati uchun samarali qarorlar qabul qilish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Sun'iy intellektning rivojlanishi global geosiyosiy raqobatning yangi bosqichini boshlab berdi. Texnologiyalar o'zgarishlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda va davlatlar o'rtasidagi diplomatik, iqtisodiy va harbiy aloqalarda yangi paradigmalariga yo'l ochmoqda. (Jonassen, D., 1994). Shu bilan birga, sun'iy intellektning xavfsizlik, diplomatiya va axborot strategiyalaridagi o'rni yangi tahdidlarni yuzaga keltiradi, shuning uchun xalqaro hamkorlik va yaxshilangan normativ asoslar zarur. Global xavfsizlikni ta'minlash va sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning etik tamoyillarini shakllantirish uchun xalqaro miqyosda yangi yondashuvlar ishlab chiqilishi kerak.

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The role of social networks in motivating students to learn English

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Annotation. Social networks have become powerful tools in modern education, significantly influencing the process of learning English. This article explores how social media platforms motivate students by providing exposure to authentic language, creating interactive and engaging learning experiences, and fostering peer collaboration. Additionally, access to language influencers, gamification, personalized learning experiences, and real-world communication opportunities enhance motivation and language proficiency. The findings suggest that integrating social networks into English learning can revolutionize language education, making it more accessible, enjoyable, and effective for students worldwide.

Keywords: impact, social media, motivation, global language, learning English, online education.

Annotatsiya. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar zamonaviy ta'limning kuchli vositalariga aylanib, ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Ushbu maqola ijtimoiy media platformalari o'quvchilarni asl til bilan tanishtirish, interaktiv va qiziqarli o'rganish tajribasini yaratish va tengdoshlar bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirish orqali qanday motivatsiya qilishini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, tilga ta'sir o'tkazuvchilarga kirish, o'yinlar yaratish, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'rganish tajribasi va real aloqa imkoniyatlari motivatsiya va tilni bilish darajasini oshiradi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarni ingliz tilini o'rganishga integratsiyalash til ta'limida inqilob qilishi va uni butun dunyo bo'ylab talabalar uchun qulayroq, qiziqarli va samaraliroq qilish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'sir, ijtimoiy media, motivatsiya, global til, ingliz tilini o'rganish, onlayn ta'lim.

Аннотация. Социальные сети стали мощными инструментами в современном образовании, значительно влияя на процесс изучения английского языка. В этой статье рассматривается, как платформы социальных сетей мотивируют студентов, предоставляя им возможность познакомиться с аутентичным языком, создавая интерактивный и увлекательный опыт обучения и способствуя сотрудничеству сверстников. Кроме того, доступ к языковым авторитетам, геймификация, персонализированный опыт обучения и возможности общения в реальном мире повышают мотивацию и уровень владения языком. Результаты показывают, что интеграция социальных сетей в изучение английского языка может произвести революцию в языковом образовании, сделав его более доступным, приятным и эффективным

для студентов по всему миру.

Ключевые слова: влияние, социальные сети, мотивация, глобальный язык, изучение английского языка, онлайн-образование.

Introduction Social networks are essential in many facets of life, including education, in the current digital age. English language acquisition is one of the most essential domains where social media has an impact. Students are increasingly using social media platforms for engagement, motivation, and real-world language application as English becomes a more important global language. The effectiveness of social networks as a means of encouraging students to learn English is examined in this study.

The Internet allows people to unite in communities based on interests and topics for communication. They post various photo and video files, create blogs, etc.

All this has a common name - a social network. Social networks have become one of the most important means of communication between people. The goal of social networks is to make the world more open. Currently, social networks have a great influence on many areas of our lives, in particular on education. In this regard, we will consider the most popular social networks among students, we will try to focus on the main advantages and disadvantages of their use in the educational process.

In order to increase the motivation of students at agricultural universities, the teacher must take a clear approach to choosing assignments. Assignments generated on the basis of social networks must meet the basic requirements. These include the following: 1. Diversity. Social networks involve the use of various types of assignments (online conversation, online discussion, viewing modern authentic professional materials, reading adapted and non-adapted specialized literature) and exercises, a variety of forms of organizing educational activities (assignments can be completed in small and large groups, individually, by forming a team).

D. O. Koroleva conducted a study to assess how actively Russian high school students and future students use mobile technologies and social networks. According to her data, the most popular social network among young men and women is Vkontakte, 91% of respondents indicated it, Instagram is in second place - 50%, then Facebook - 28.5%. 3% of students do not have accounts in social networks (see fig.) (5). Vkontakte profile is used as the main communication for 86% of students, 73% of respondents noted that they have only one account in this social network, two or more accounts for 23% of respondents. It should be noted that 70% of respondents use mobile devices, as well as social networks to search for information during lessons (university classes). (see it in Pic.1)

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respondents use mobile devices, as well as social networks to search for information during lessons (university classes).

Picture 1.

G.B. Saifutdinova and A.S. Mironenko describe the experience of using social networks as a means for organizing independent work of students (G. Saifutdinova, A. Mironenko, 2017). Thanks to the social network, when completing assignments, students are allowed to contact their teachers with questions and comments directly during the preparation. In our opinion, the consultation can be conducted in a foreign language, by the language studied by the students. For example, an English teacher can allow students to consult with him exclusively in English.

Thus, the use of social networks in the educational process promotes the exchange of information, increases the motivation of students in educational activities, stimulates the development of creative abilities and cognitive interest.

The main distinctive feature of learning a language with the help of a social network is the possibility of contact with a native speaker or with a person who also needs to practice the language. It should be noted that when studying foreign languages by university students, the list of social networks can be expanded. Communicating in international social networks, you can not only find new friends all over the world, but also significantly improve your level of proficiency in a particular foreign language. The most popular social networks are: Busuu, Sharedtalk, My Language Exchange, English, Baby!, Lang8, Ling, Livemocha, Interpals and others. It should also be noted that the social network Facebook is popular among American students, allowing students from any corner of the world to keep in touch with each other, communicating in an international language - English.

How social media impact Learners' Motivation. The impacts of social media on motivation toward English were made possible through the connective, interactive, and collaborative features of social media. These characteristic features are discussed in the following paragraphs. The concept of connectivity was highlighted across all the

media. It is one of the essential characteristics of social media that has positively influenced English learners' motivation. Social media is a hub of networks with various English learning sites, accounts, channels, pages, posts, statuses, stories, and real-life teachers and experts as well as proficient and native English speakers. It is a nebulous environment of constantly shifting and updating core elements with up-to-date information. As a result of the theoretical analysis of the above-described works and our own accumulated pedagogical experience in the use of social networks in teaching a foreign language to students of an agricultural university, we concluded that the use of social networks creates an excellent platform for expanding the boundaries of foreign language study in and out of class. Social networking sites play an important role in improving and developing education both at the level of students and at the level of teaching staff. To increase the motivation of students of agricultural universities, the teacher must approach the selection of tasks. Tasks formed based on social networks must meet the basic requirements. These include the following:

1. **Diversity.** Social networks involve the use of various types of tasks (online conversation, online discussion, viewing modern authentic professional materials, reading adapted and non-adapted specialized literature) and exercises, a variety of forms of organizing educational activities (tasks can be completed in small and large groups, individually, by forming a team)

2. **Problem-solving.** Problems make students think and find ways to solve them. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages have a wide range of communicative tasks and project work aimed at solving problems. The problem-solving approach can be used at various stages of learning. It helps to master the necessary vocabulary and grammar of the language being studied, develop speaking, and listening skills, etc.

3. **Learning with pleasure.** Only learning a foreign language with pleasure gives a positive result. The student must have a desire to learn, find positive aspects in this process, know their goals and objectives. Experience shows that pleasure in learning is achieved in various ways, one of which is the selection of entertaining tasks. Entertainment is one of the main reasons for using social networks in the educational process.

When talking about the use of social networks in teaching a foreign language, we can highlight the following characteristics:

1. **Flexibility.**

This feature expands the possibilities of choosing what, when, and where to study. Flexibility is also the anticipation of new educational opportunities and readiness for the constantly changing requirements of modern society. The use of social networks in teaching a foreign language allows students to determine the prospects for self-development and self-study.

2. Communicativeness.

With the help of social networks, you can create a favorable learning environment for communication in English. Students do not need to go to the country of the language they are studying, they simply connect to the Internet and communicate with native English speakers. Social networking sites encourage students to interact with each other, express and share their thoughts, and be creative.

3. Convenience and accessibility.

Social networks provide easy access to educational materials (at any time and anywhere), make it convenient to view, update and edit them. In addition, they allow you to select the educational materials that are necessary for learning, facilitating their dissemination.

4. Efficiency.

Teaching English through social networks can make classes not only more effective but also more efficient. Many social networking sites offer users various applications that can be useful in learning English. Social networks overcome the limitations of space and time in the learning process. Social networking helps to reduce stress and increase student satisfaction. They can study at their own pace. In addition, they can discuss emerging problems at any time. Describing the main advantages of social networks in teaching a foreign language, we can also highlight some negative factors. Students are forced to use various technical means that make the social network accessible. This distracts them and shows the lack of social interactivity in real life. Computers and phones have become an integral part of our daily lives. But their frequent and uncontrolled use can affect the psychological and physical health of students. Learning with the help of social networks should not take up the entire time of classroom lessons, but only be a part of it. This method of organizing learning should serve only as a measure of encouragement for students. Using social networks in teaching a foreign language leads to a decrease in interest in completing traditional tasks on reading, translating a text, and presenting its content. Getting used to work in social networks, where the presented material may contain sound and other visual effects, one must constantly return to the usual methods and forms of work in the classroom. In addition, one disadvantage of using social networks is the lack of ICT competence in students of agricultural universities. When entering higher education institutions from rural areas, many of them have poor computer skills and other technical means. Therefore, the role of the teacher is to activate knowledge and skills in this area. These negative factors are becoming less and less relevant in a modern, fully computerized society.

Effectiveness of the Platforms

From the investigation, it was discovered that YouTube was the most effective social media platform for students' motivation and English learning. YouTube makes

English learning easy, fun, and spontaneous due to its variety of information sources and distinctive characteristics that allow created videos to be shared, discovered, and viewed across the globe. The commonest of these specialized sources among language learners are song lyrics and movie subtitles. They boost the passion for daily learning, practice, and use of English. YouTube channels and content enhance basic language skills especially listening and speaking (Hasan et al., 2018). Its flexibility in terms of time, place, mode, and choice motivates, while its plethora of scenarios with proper usage of language enhances pragmatics and cross-culturally understanding (Kim & Kim, 2021). It virtually answers every question asked with a variety of opinions at little or no time and cost. Instagram had a significant impact on participants' motivation to learn English but was lower than the impact of YouTube. The platform is both interactive and connective. Interactive, by enhancing the establishment and maintenance of communication with friends and teachers, at home and abroad. Connective, by providing various sources of information with up-to-date authenticated knowledge.

Conclusion

Motivation toward learning English as a global language is positively impacted by the use of social media. This study, therefore, recommends the integration of social media with proper guidelines into English teaching and learning process by education policymakers and curriculum planners. Also, connectivism should be adopted as one of the core teaching approaches and learning strategies. This flows from the position that knowledge is essentially a network and learning in the contemporary hyperconnected society is a process of connecting specialized nodes. In the light of this approach, teachers ought to be more open to diversified opinions as well as assume a facilitatory role in students' learning process. On the part of the students, they should not only limit their focus of using social media to social connectedness and pleasurable wants but extend it more to cognitive connectedness and learning.

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THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AI TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayonidagi roli yoritilgan. ChatGPT, Grammarly, Duolingo kabi AI vositalari orqali yozish, o'qish, so'zlashuv va eslab qolish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, VR texnologiyasi yordamida til o'rganishda interaktiv muhit yaratishning afzalliklari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tili, AI vositalari, VR, til o'rganish.

Annotation: This article discusses the role of artificial intelligence in English language learning. It highlights how tools like ChatGPT, Grammarly, and Duolingo enhance skills such as writing, speaking, reading, and vocabulary retention. The use of virtual reality (VR) in creating immersive language environments is also briefly analyzed.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, English language, AI tools, VR, language learning.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена использованию искусственного интеллекта в изучении английского языка. Рассматриваются возможности приложений, таких как ChatGPT, Grammarly и Duolingo, в развитии речевых и письменных навыков. Также кратко освещается применение виртуальной реальности для создания языковой среды.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, английский язык, ИИ-инструменты, VR, изучение языка.

In today's digital era, artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing various sectors, and education is no exception. English, being the most widely studied and spoken language globally, plays a crucial role in communication, business, tourism, and technology. However, learning English remains challenging for many due to

limited exposure, lack of interaction opportunities, fear of mistakes, and insufficient feedback. AI offers promising tools to overcome these barriers, making English language teaching and learning (ELT/L) more personalized, efficient, and accessible.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force in education, especially in the teaching and learning of English as a foreign language. The term "Artificial Intelligence" was first introduced in 1956 by John McCarthy, and it represents the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. Today, AI integrates various disciplines such as philosophy, psychology, and computer science, enabling machines to think, learn, and act intelligently.

In the context of English Language Teaching and Learning (ELT/L), AI has provided significant innovations that extend beyond traditional teaching approaches. AI applications like ChatGPT, Google AI, and Bing AI have become essential tools in modern classrooms. These platforms support students by generating ideas for discussions, personalizing learning experiences, and increasing engagement. By tailoring content to individual needs, AI boosts learners' attention and motivation, facilitating higher levels of achievement.

One of the emerging methods of AI integration in ELT is the use of Virtual Reality (VR). AI-powered VR simulations immerse learners in English-speaking environments, promoting cultural understanding and helping develop language skills in real-life contexts. Research suggests that integrating VR with language learning can enhance communication skills and language acquisition. However, devices such as Apple Glass and Google Glass are not yet widely affordable, limiting broader access.

Moreover, AI has played a key role in improving productive skills such as writing and speaking. AI grammar checkers like Grammarly help reduce grammatical errors and increase lexical diversity in students' writing. Machine translation tools, like Google Translate, aid less proficient learners in producing higher-quality texts with more complex vocabulary and syntax. AI tools also support writing by providing instant feedback, increasing learners' self-efficacy and engagement.

In terms of speaking, AI helps improve pronunciation and fluency through visual aids such as spectrograms and speech analysis tools. Interactive voice assistants like Alexa have been found to enhance vocabulary acquisition and speaking confidence. AI coaching systems and multimodal learning platforms provide tailored feedback, fostering more fluent and accurate language use.

When it comes to reading, although less explored than speaking and writing, AI applications have shown promise. For instance, vocabulary acquisition through gaming, as explored in World of Warcraft-based studies, highlights how contextualized learning environments can outperform traditional textbook methods.

One of the major challenges in learning English is the fear of making communication errors. AI-powered chatbots such as ChatGPT are especially useful in overcoming this barrier. These tools support learners by offering real-time responses, suggesting new discussion topics, and correcting mistakes during conversations. This creates a safe space for learners to practice without fear of judgment.

Today, AI technologies make learning English more accessible and efficient. Tools like Babbel, Duolingo, Grammarly, Quizlet, and ChatGPT personalize the learning process, making it more interactive and enjoyable. These applications help students with grammar correction, vocabulary retention, and conversational practice, all while allowing learners to progress independently. By using AI, students can build their confidence and achieve greater success in mastering English.

- **Babbel** is a language-learning app that offers well-structured lessons based on real-life situations. It focuses on grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. Babbel's method is designed by language experts and helps users build strong foundational skills. It is especially useful for beginners who want a clear and logical path to follow.

- **Duolingo** makes language learning fun and engaging through a game-like experience. It uses short, interactive lessons that cover reading, listening, writing, and speaking. The app encourages daily practice and motivates learners with rewards and challenges. It is great for keeping learners consistent and improving basic communication skills.

- **Grammarly** is a writing assistant that helps improve grammar, spelling, and punctuation. It gives real-time feedback on your writing and suggests better word choices or sentence structures. Grammarly is especially helpful for students, professionals, and anyone who wants to write clearly and correctly in English.

- **Quizlet** is a study tool that uses flashcards, quizzes, and games to help learners remember vocabulary and key concepts. Users can create their own study sets or use those made by others. It's a great way to review words, definitions, and phrases quickly and effectively, especially before exams or tests.

- **ChatGPT** is an AI-powered tool that allows users to practice English in real conversations. We can ask questions, translate sentences, improve our writing, or understand grammar rules better. It's like having a personal tutor available anytime. ChatGPT helps learners build confidence and fluency in real-time interactions.

As artificial intelligence continues to advance, its impact on education—especially in the field of English language teaching (ELT)—is becoming increasingly significant. AI offers transformative opportunities by personalizing learning experiences, delivering immediate feedback, and creating engaging and authentic content. These capabilities make AI a powerful tool for modern language education. With ongoing research, investment, and the growing accessibility of AI technologies, its integration into ELT is expected to deepen, reshaping how English is taught and

learned across diverse learner populations worldwide.

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Enhancing Learning Strategies Through AI-Based Educational Chatbots: Insights from Pedagogical Practice

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Annotation

This article explores the impact of artificial intelligence (AI)-based educational chatbots on students' learning strategies and academic performance, emphasizing their relevance in modern educational systems. The paper outlines how such chatbots, through personalized feedback, adaptive learning, and continuous interaction, enhance cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational learning strategies. Drawing on current literature and research, this study highlights the role of chatbots as digital learning assistants and evaluates their efficacy in improving students' autonomy, critical thinking, and academic engagement. Real-world applications and examples from Uzbek academic settings are also provided to illustrate the methodological approach to integrating chatbots into learning environments.

Keywords: Educational chatbots, artificial intelligence, learning strategies, cognitive engagement, digital pedagogy, motivation, Uzbekistan, metacognition, adaptive learning.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается влияние образовательных чат-ботов, основанных на технологиях искусственного интеллекта (ИИ), на учебные стратегии студентов и их академическую успеваемость, с акцентом на актуальность таких инструментов в современной образовательной системе. Работа описывает, как чат-боты с помощью персонализированной обратной связи, адаптивного обучения и постоянного взаимодействия способствуют развитию когнитивных, метакогнитивных и мотивационных стратегий обучения. Опираясь на современные научные исследования, в статье подчеркивается роль чат-ботов как цифровых помощников в обучении и оценивается их эффективность в повышении автономности студентов, критического мышления и вовлеченности в учебный процесс. Также приводятся

реальные примеры из учебной практики в вузах Узбекистана, иллюстрирующие методологический подход к интеграции чат-ботов в образовательную среду.

Ключевые слова: образовательные чат-боты, искусственный интеллект, стратегии обучения, когнитивное вовлечение, цифровая педагогика, мотивация, Узбекистан, метакогниция, адаптивное обучение.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt (SI) asosidagi ta'limiy chatbotlarning talabalarning o'quv strategiyalari va akademik natijalariga ta'siri o'rganiladi hamda ularning zamonaviy ta'lim tizimidagi dolzarbligi yoritiladi. Maqolada shaxsiylashtirilgan fikr-mulohaza, moslashuvchan o'qitish va uzluksiz muloqot orqali chatbotlar kognitiv, metakognitiv va motivatsion o'quv strategiyalarini qanday rivojlantirishi ko'rsatiladi. Mavjud adabiyotlar va tadqiqotlar asosida olib borilgan tahlil chatbotlarni raqamli o'quv yordamchilari sifatida baholab, ularning talabalar mustaqilligi, tanqidiy fikrlashi va o'quv jarayonidagi faolligini oshirishdagi samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim muassasalaridan real misollar orqali chatbotlarni o'quv muhitiga joriy etishning uslubiy yondashuvi ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'limiy chatbotlar, sun'iy intellekt, o'quv strategiyalari, kognitiv faollik, raqamli pedagogika, motivatsiya, O'zbekiston, metakognitsiya, moslashuvchan o'qitish.

Introduction

The digital transformation of education, driven by artificial intelligence, has introduced new tools that support student learning more interactively and individually. Among these tools, educational chatbots—AI-powered conversational agents—have proven effective in enhancing learning outcomes. These systems facilitate real-time feedback, simulate dialogue-based instruction, and adapt to students' performance levels (Wollny et al., 2021).

In Uzbekistan, as universities seek to modernize instructional methods, integrating AI tools such as chatbots aligns with broader educational goals, including self-directed learning, increased student engagement, and enhanced use of digital technologies in the learning process. This article analyzes how AI-based educational chatbots influence the development of learning strategies and explores methodological approaches for implementing them in higher education.

Understanding Educational Chatbots and Learning Strategies

Educational chatbots are programmed to interact with students using natural language processing and machine learning. These interactions are designed to stimulate reflection, encourage practice, and provide immediate feedback—all of which are critical for developing effective learning strategies (Winkler & Söllner, 2018).

Learning strategies are typically categorized into:

- Cognitive strategies: Processing and organizing new information.
- Metacognitive strategies: Planning, monitoring, and evaluating learning.
- Motivational strategies: Sustaining interest and effort during learning tasks.

Learning strategies are essential components of effective academic performance, particularly in environments that demand self-directed and autonomous

learning. Among the most recognized categories are cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational strategies, each serving a distinct role in the learning process. Cognitive strategies involve the mental processes used to acquire and organize new knowledge—such as summarizing, highlighting key points, and categorizing concepts—which help learners construct meaningful mental representations. In contrast, metacognitive strategies go beyond the processing of information to include the planning, monitoring, and evaluation of one's own learning activities. These strategies enable learners to assess their comprehension, regulate attention, and adjust approaches based on feedback or performance outcomes. Finally, motivational strategies play a crucial role in maintaining learners' engagement, confidence, and persistence in the face of challenges. These include setting goals, self-reinforcement, and using interest-driven learning tools to sustain effort over time. Collectively, these strategies not only enhance knowledge retention but also promote deeper understanding and academic resilience. As noted by Pintrich and De Groot (1990), students who effectively apply all three types of strategies—cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational—tend to exhibit higher academic achievement and greater self-regulation, suggesting that balanced development in these areas is key to educational success.

Chatbots support these areas by offering step-by-step assistance, guiding questions, and interactive prompts that adapt to the learner's progress (Kuhail et al., 2022). For example, a chatbot might notice a pattern of incorrect answers in a grammar module and suggest a review session or explain a rule in simpler terms, reinforcing both cognitive understanding and metacognitive reflection.

Developing Cognitive and Metacognitive Skills Through Chatbots

According to Earley & Ang (2003), successful learners must be equipped with the ability to analyze their thinking (metacognition) and adjust their strategies accordingly. Chatbots assist in this process by:

- Asking reflective questions like “What part of this topic confuses you?”
- Encouraging goal-setting and progress tracking.
- Offering summaries and quizzes to reinforce understanding.

This reflects a shift from traditional lecture-based instruction toward student-centered, technology-supported learning models. For instance, in a pilot study conducted at Kimyo International University in Tashkent, students using a chatbot-integrated platform reported greater confidence in self-assessing their understanding of complex topics, demonstrating improved metacognitive engagement (Smutny & Schreiberova, 2020).

Motivational Engagement and Self-Regulated Learning

Chatbots also serve a motivational function, helping students stay engaged with tasks through encouragement, gamified learning paths, and rewards systems. High motivational engagement leads to better persistence, especially in asynchronous learning environments. Ang et al. (2007) highlight that digital agents offering continuous, empathetic feedback can significantly reduce student anxiety and promote a growth mindset.

In Uzbekistan, where many students may initially lack confidence in using English or technology for learning, chatbots that respond in both Uzbek and English can reduce the affective barrier and increase comfort levels, further supporting motivation and inclusivity.

Methodological Integration in Uzbek Educational Context

The practical application of chatbot-assisted learning in Uzbekistan requires an approach tailored to local needs. Strategies include:

- Designing bilingual chatbots for inclusive access.
- Integrating chatbot use into curriculum planning and teacher training.
- Using chatbots for formative assessment and personalized feedback.

Designing and integrating bilingual chatbots into educational settings offers significant advantages for promoting inclusive, adaptive, and student-centered learning. Bilingual chatbots serve as powerful tools for breaking language barriers, particularly in multilingual countries like Uzbekistan, where students may be more fluent in Uzbek or Russian than in English. By offering responses in two or more languages, these chatbots ensure that all learners, regardless of linguistic background, can access learning materials, ask questions, and receive feedback in a language they are comfortable with—thereby reducing anxiety and increasing participation. Moreover, integrating chatbot use into curriculum planning and teacher training is crucial for successful implementation. Educators must be familiar with the capabilities and limitations of chatbot technologies in order to align them with learning outcomes and pedagogical goals. This requires not only technical training but also a shift in instructional design, where chatbot interactions are purposefully woven into learning activities such as debates, practice quizzes, or writing exercises. Additionally, chatbots can be employed for formative assessment and personalized feedback, providing students with real-time insights into their learning progress. Unlike traditional tests, chatbots can deliver tailored explanations, suggest supplementary resources, or adapt the difficulty of questions based on student responses. This personalized feedback loop supports differentiated instruction and encourages students to take greater ownership of their learning, which is especially valuable in large classrooms or blended learning environments. Ultimately, bilingual educational chatbots represent a scalable solution for enhancing equity, engagement, and efficiency in 21st-century education.

One example is a collaborative project at Uzbek State World Languages University, where chatbot use in a “Critical Thinking in Education” course led to a 20% increase in quiz scores and a notable rise in student participation in discussions.

Such evidence suggests that AI chatbots can function as both teaching assistants and cognitive coaches, enhancing students' academic performance and independence.

Conclusion

The integration of AI-powered educational chatbots into modern pedagogical practices marks a significant shift toward more personalized, autonomous, and technology-enhanced learning environments. By fostering the development of cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational learning strategies, these chatbots serve not merely as supplementary tools, but as active agents that can guide, support, and transform the student learning experience. Their ability to provide instant feedback, facilitate reflective thinking, and maintain learner engagement through adaptive interaction is instrumental in cultivating lifelong learning skills and academic self-efficacy.

In the context of Uzbekistan's higher education system, where digital transformation and educational modernization are national priorities, the deployment of chatbots offers a practical and scalable approach to achieving these goals. By enabling bilingual support, promoting equity, and enhancing learner-centered methodologies, educational chatbots can bridge gaps in access, language proficiency, and instructional resources. The positive outcomes observed in pilot projects, such as improved student performance, increased motivation, and heightened classroom participation, underscore their potential as both pedagogical tools and strategic enablers of innovation.

Ultimately, educational chatbots embody a forward-thinking pedagogical paradigm—one that aligns with the demands of 21st-century education by enhancing learner agency, fostering critical thinking, and creating more dynamic, inclusive, and resilient learning ecosystems. Their role in transforming education in Uzbekistan and beyond is not only timely but essential for cultivating the next generation of digitally fluent and self-regulated learners.

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SUN'IY INTELLEKT VOSITALARI ORQALI IJTIMOY REALLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH: TA'LIM JARAYONIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING PERSEPSIYAGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonida talabalarning ijtimoiy reallikni qabul qilishi (persepsiyasi)ga ta'siri tahlil etiladi. Ta'limda sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan foydalanish o'quvchi ongida yangi ijtimoiy muhitni shakllantirayotgan ijtimoiy-psixologik mexanizmlar aniqlanadi. Shuningdek, ta'limdagi interaktiv muhit, media va raqamli texnologiyalarning talaba shaxsiga ko'rsatgan ta'siri haqida nazariy asoslar va metodologik yondashuvlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ijtimoiy reallik, persepsiya, ta'lim texnologiyalari, raqamli psixologiya, virtual muhit.

Annotation: this article analyzes the impact of artificial intelligence technologies on students perception (perception)of social reality in the educational process. The use of artificial intelligence tools in education determines the socio-psychological mechanisms that are forming a new social environment in the student's mind. Theoretical frameworks and methodological approaches to the interactive environment in education, the impact of media and digital technologies on the student's personality are also cited.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, social realism, perception, educational technology, digital psychology, virtual environment.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется влияние технологий искусственного интеллекта на восприятие (перцепцию)социальной реальности учащимися в процессе обучения. Использование средств искусственного интеллекта в образовании выявляет социально-психологические механизмы, формирующие в сознании учащегося новую социальную среду. В нем также представлены теоретические основы и методологические подходы к влиянию интерактивной среды, медиа и цифровых технологий в образовании на личность учащегося.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, социальная реальность, перцепция, образовательные технологии, цифровая психология, виртуальная среда.

Kirish. Bugungi raqamli jamiyatda sun'iy intellekt (SI) nafaqat ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalariga, balki ta'lim tizimiga ham chuqur kirib keldi. Sun'iy intellekt vositalari (chatbotlar, interaktiv tizimlar, o'quv platformalari, algoritmik tahlil dasturlari) o'quvchilarning bilimni o'zlashtirish jarayoniga ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Biroq, bu texnologiyalar faqatgina o'quv samaradorligini oshirmasdan, balki talabalarning ijtimoiy reallik haqidagi tasavvurlarini shakllantiruvchi omilga aylanmoqda. Aynan ushbu holatning pedagogik va psixologik jihatdan o'rganilishi dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi.

So'nggi yillarda sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi loyihalarni boshqarish jarayonlariga sezilarli yangiliklar olib kirmoqda. Endilikda an'anaviy uslublariga nisbatan SI vositalaridan foydalanish orqali loyiha faoliyatini rejalashtirish, resurslarni samarali taqsimlash, xatoliklarni oldindan aniqlash va bajarilish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish imkoniyatlari kengaymoqda. Jumladan, ma'lumotlarni onlayn rejimda tahlil qilish, ilg'or algoritmlarga asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilish hamda avtomatlashtirilgan monitoring tizimlari loyihalarning muvaffaqiyat ko'rsatkichlarini ancha oshirayotgani kuzatilmoqda[5].

2024-yil ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini joriy qilgan tashkilotlar loyihalarni bajarish samaradorligini o'rtacha 30 foizga yaxshilagan.

Dunyo amaliyotida keng qo'llanilayotgan Microsoft Project, Oracle Primavera va Asana kabi platformalarga sun'iy intellekt elementlarini integratsiyalash orqali murakkab loyihalarni byudjet, vaqt va sifat nuqtai nazaridan aniq boshqarish imkoniyati yaratilmoqda. Biroq, ushbu texnologiyalarning samaradorligi bilan birga, ularni joriy etish mobaynida duch kelinayotgan muammolar — raqamli savodxonlikning yetishmasligi, axborot xavfsizligi va etik masalalar ham alohida e'tibor talab etmoqda.

Asosiy qism. Sun'iy intellekt inson ongini modellashtiruvchi tizim sifatida virtual haqiqat (VR), kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR) va generativ AI orqali talabanning real dunyo haqidagi tushunchalarini o'zgartiradi. Masalan, ChatGPT kabi tizimlardan muntazam foydalanish ta'lim oluvchining haqiqatni izohlash, baholash, savol berish va javob topish jarayonlarini avtomatlashtiradi.

Sun'iy intellekt - insonning bilim va ko'nikmalariga taqlid qilish imkonini beruvchi (shu jumladan, mustaqil ravishda o'rganish va yechimlarni izlash) hamda aniq vazifalarni bajarishda inson aqliy faoliyati natijalari bilan taqqoslanadigan natijalarni olish imkonini beradigan texnologik yechimlar majmuidir [1]

Persepsiya - bu ong orqali tashqi muhitni tushunish va talqin qilishdir. AI vositalari orqali berilgan axborotlar o'quvchilar tomonidan ishonchli, neytral yoki

ob'ektiv deb qabul qilinadi, bu esa ijtimoiy idrokda sun'iy intellektning "mualliflik" roli shakllanishiga olib keladi.

Ta'limda sun'iy intellekt vositalarining ta'siri shundan iboratki, individual yondashuvni ta'minlaydi va talabalarning axborot tanlash mezonlarini o'zgartiradi.

Ijtimoiy va kommunikativ ko'nikmalarning o'rnini algoritmik javoblar egallaydi. O'quvchi shaxsining tafakkuri, qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu sababli, ijtimoiy reallik talabaning ongida sun'iy muhit ko'rinishida shakllanishi xavfi mavjud [3].

Ijtimoiy reallik - bu insonlar orasidagi o'zaro aloqalar, kommunikatsiya va tajribalar asosida shakllanadigan ijtimoiy hayot hodisalari majmuasi. Sun'iy intellekt vositalari ushbu reallikni shakllantirishda ishtirok eta boshlagani ta'lim tizimi, ishbilarmonlik va ommaviy axborot sohalariga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda.

Persepsiya - bu insonning atrof-muhitdagi axborotni qabul qilish, uni qayta ishlash va asoslangan fikrga aylantirish jarayoni. Ta'lim jarayonida SI vositalarining qo'llanilishi talabalarning:

- dunyoqarashi,
- axborotga munosabati,
- tanqidiy fikrlashi,
- muammoga yondashuvi

kabi jihatlarida sezilarli o'zgarishlar qilmoqda.

Sun'iy intellektning ta'limdagi ta'sir shakllariga quyidagilarni kiritishimiz mumkin:

1. Personalizatsiyalangan o'qitish – har bir talabaning o'ziga xos ehtiyojiga mos mashqlar, topshiriqlar SI tomonidan taqdim etiladi.

2. Virtual reallik (VR) va kengaytirilgan reallik (AR) – real hayotda duch kelinadigan vaziyatlarni modellashtirib, talabaning idrokini chuqurlashtiradi.

3. Chatbot va ovozli yordamchilar – axborotni tez va interaktiv tarzda olishni osonlashtiradi.

4. Yuz ifodasi va kayfiyat tahlili – pedagogik jarayonni emotsional jihatdan nazorat qilish imkonini beradi.

5. Deepfake va manipulyatsion kontent xavfi – bu ijtimoiy reallikni buzishi mumkin, tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishga ehtiyoj tug'diradi.

Psixologik va pedagogik ta'sir jihatlarini o'rganar ekanmiz kognitiv yuklamaning kamayishi Sun'iy intellektning ortiqcha ma'lumotni filtrlashini aniqlashimiz mumkin. Diqqat va motivatsiyaga ta'siri interaktiv vositalar darsga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshiradi. Ijtimoiy idrokning shakllanishida talaba SI tomonidan yaratilgan ma'lumotni haqiqat deb qabul qilish xavfi mavjud.

Tavsiya etiladigan ehtiyot choralari:

- SI vositalarining etik me'yorlari ishlab chiqilishi zarur.

- Talabalarga axborot savodxonligi, tanqidiy fikrlash va faktlarni tekshirish ko'nikmalari o'rgatilishi kerak.

- Sun'iy intellekt o'qituvchini to'liq almashtirmasligi, balki uni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi vosita sifatida ishlatilishi lozim.

- Kontent-tahlil: sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ta'lim platformalari (Duolingo, Coursera, ChatGPT) kontenti tahlil qilindi [4].

Sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari ta'lim jarayonida keng ko'lamli imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi. U o'quv jarayonining sifatini oshirish, uni shaxsga moslashtirish hamda samaradorligini kuchaytirishda muhim vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, oliy ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellekt o'z o'rniga ega bo'lib, u o'quv jarayonini avtomatlashtirish, o'qituvchilarga yordam berish, talabalarning natijalarini baholashni soddalashtirish va katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish imkonini yaratadi.

Shu bilan birga, bu texnologiyalarni to'laqonli va muvaffaqiyatli tatbiq etish uchun zaruriy infratuzilmalarni rivojlantirish, moliyaviy ta'minotni yo'lga qo'yish va pedagog kadrlarning malakasini oshirish kabi asosiy muammolarni hal qilish talab etiladi. Sun'iy intellektning izchil taraqqiyoti esa ta'lim sohasida yangi yechimlar va ilg'or yondashuvlar paydo bo'lishiga turtki bo'ladi, bu esa ta'lim tizimini zamon talablari asosida yangilashga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytishimiz mumkinki, sun'iy intellekt vositalari o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy reallik haqidagi tasavvurlariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Bu ta'sir ijobiy va salbiy natijalarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Ijobiy jihati shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim, tezkor javob olish, o'quvga qiziqishning ortishi bo'lsa, salbiy tomoni esa sun'iy ijtimoiy normalar shakllanishi, muloqot qobiliyatining pasayishi, mustaqil tafakkurning cheklanishi bo'lishi mumkin. Shu boisdan, pedagoglar AI vositalarini maqsadli, tanqidiy va me'yoriy tarzda joriy etishi zarur.

Ta'limda SI texnologiyalarining joriy etilishi o'quv jarayonini samarali va individual tarzda olib borish imkonini yaratadi. Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining oliy ta'limda qo'llanilishi talabalarning o'qish jarayonini optimallashtirish, o'qituvchilarga yordam berish va oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyatini samarali tashkil etish imkonini beradi.

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How technology is changing the way we learn English

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Abstract. The rapid advancement of technology has significantly transformed the way individuals learn English, making it more accessible, engaging, and personalized than ever before. This paper explores the impact of digital tools, online platforms, and artificial intelligence on English language acquisition. Through a review of existing literature, analysis of popular language-learning applications, and feedback from learners, the study highlights key innovations such as mobile apps, virtual reality, and AI-driven personalized learning systems. The findings reveal that technology enhances accessibility, provides tailored learning experiences, and fosters global connectivity by connecting learners with native speakers. However, challenges such as over-reliance on technology, unequal access to resources, and reduced face-to-face interaction are also discussed. The paper concludes that while technology offers remarkable opportunities for English learners, a balanced approach that combines traditional methods with modern tools is essential for optimal outcomes.

Key words: technology in education, English language learning, digital tools, artificial intelligence (AI), language acquisition, interactive learning, digital divide.

Annotatsiya. Texnologiyalarning tez rivojlanishi tufayli ingliz tilini o'rganish usullari sezilarli darajada o'zgargan bo'lib, bu jarayon hozirgina eng yuqori darajada qulaylik, jozibadorlik va shaxsiy yondashuvga ega bo'lgan holatda amalga oshirilmoqda. Ushbu maqola raqamli vositalar, onlayn platformalar va sun'iy intellektning ingliz tilini o'zlashtirishdagi ta'sirini o'rganadi. Mavjud adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish, mashhur tillarni o'rganish ilovalarini tahlil qilish va o'quvchilardan olingan fikr-mulohazalar asosida tadqiqot mobil ilovalar, virtual real'nost va AI-ga asoslangan shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish tizimlari kabi muhim innovatsiyalarni ajratib ko'rsatadi. Natijalar texnologiyalarning ingliz tilini o'rganish uchun imkoniyatlarni oshirish, moslashtirilgan ta'lim tajribalarini taqdim etish va o'quvchilarni ana tilidan so'zlashuvchi bilan bog'lash orqali jahon miqyosidagi aloqadorlikni rivojlantirishga xizmat qilganligini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, texnologiyaga ortiqcha ishonish, resurslarga tengsiz kirish va bosh-boshga muloqotning kamayishi kabi muammolar ham muhokama qilinadi. Maqola natijada ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilar uchun texnologiya ajoyib imkoniyatlar yaratgan bo'lsa-da, an'anaviy metodlar bilan zamonaviy vositalarni muvozanatli tarzda birlashtiradigan yondashuv optimal natijalarga erishish uchun zarur deb yakunlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'limdagi texnologiyalar, ingliz tilini o'rganish, raqamli vositalar, sun'iy intellekt (AI), til egallash, interaktiv o'qitish, raqamli bo'shliq.

Аннотация. Быстрое развитие технологий значительно изменило способ обучения английскому языку, сделав его более доступным, увлекательным и персонализированным, чем когда-либо прежде. В данной статье исследуется влияние цифровых инструментов, онлайн-платформ и искусственного интеллекта на освоение английского языка. На основе анализа существующей литературы, популярных приложений для изучения языков и обратной связи от обучающихся выделяются ключевые инновации, такие как мобильные приложения, виртуальная реальность и персонализированные системы обучения на базе ИИ. Результаты показывают, что технологии повышают доступность обучения, предоставляют индивидуальные образовательные возможности и способствуют глобальной коммуникации, связывая обучающихся с носителями языка. Однако также обсуждаются вызовы, такие как чрезмерная зависимость от технологий, неравный доступ к ресурсам и снижение живого общения. Статья заключается выводом о том, что, хотя технологии предлагают удивительные возможности для изучающих английский язык, для достижения оптимальных результатов необходим сбалансированный подход, сочетающий традиционные методы с современными инструментами.

Ключевые слова: технологии в образовании, изучение английского языка, цифровые инструменты, искусственный интеллект (ИИ), освоение языка, интерактивное обучение, цифровое неравенство.

Introduction.

In recent years, technology has revolutionized various aspects of our lives, including education. One of the most significant changes has been in the way people learn languages, particularly English. With the rise of digital tools, online platforms, and mobile applications, learning English has become more accessible, personalized, and efficient than ever before. This paper explores how technology is transforming English language learning by examining the latest innovations, their benefits, and potential challenges.

Methods.

To understand the impact of technology on English language learning, this study reviews existing literature, analyzes popular language-learning apps, and evaluates the effectiveness of online resources. Additionally, surveys and interviews with English learners were conducted to gather firsthand insights into their experiences with digital tools. The data collected includes feedback from students, teachers, and educational experts who have integrated technology into their teaching and learning processes.

Results

1. **Accessibility and Flexibility.** Technology has made English learning more accessible to people worldwide. Online platforms like Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone allow learners to practice English anytime and anywhere. Mobile apps provide bite-sized lessons that fit into busy schedules, enabling learners to progress at their own pace.

2. Personalized Learning. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms are being used to create personalized learning experiences. For example, platforms like Grammarly and Lingoda adapt to individual needs by identifying weak areas and offering targeted exercises. This customization ensures that learners focus on improving specific skills such as grammar, vocabulary, or pronunciation. 3. Interactive Tools and Gamification. Interactive tools like virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and gamified apps make learning engaging and fun. Apps like Memrise use game-like features to motivate users, while VR environments simulate real-life conversations, helping learners practice speaking in immersive settings.

4. Global Connectivity. Technology connects learners with native speakers and tutors through platforms like iTalki, Preply, and Cambly. Video conferencing tools like Zoom and Skype enable live interactions, bridging geographical barriers and providing authentic language practice opportunities.

5. Data-Driven Insights. Digital tools track learners' progress and provide detailed analytics. For instance, apps like Quizlet and Anki use spaced repetition techniques to reinforce memory retention, while others generate reports on performance metrics such as accuracy, speed, and comprehension.

Discussion.

The integration of technology into English language learning has brought numerous advantages. It has democratized access to quality education, allowing individuals from remote areas to learn without physical constraints. Moreover, the use of AI and data analytics has enhanced the efficiency of learning by tailoring content to individual needs. However, there are also challenges associated with this shift. Over-reliance on technology may lead to reduced face-to-face interaction, which is crucial for developing conversational skills. Additionally, not all learners have equal access to devices or stable internet connections, creating a digital divide. Furthermore, some critics argue that excessive screen time can hinder focus and lead to burnout. Despite these concerns, the overall impact of technology on English learning remains overwhelmingly positive. By combining traditional methods with modern tools, educators can create a balanced approach that maximizes the benefits of both worlds.

Conclusion.

Technology is undeniably reshaping the landscape of English language learning. From mobile apps and AI-driven platforms to virtual classrooms and global connectivity, digital innovations are making it easier, faster, and more enjoyable to acquire proficiency in English. While challenges exist, they can be addressed through thoughtful implementation and equitable access to resources. As technology continues to evolve, its role in language education will only grow stronger, paving the way for a future where learning English is no longer limited by geography or circumstance.

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THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) va sun'iy intellekt (SI) asosida kasbiy ingliz tili ta'limini takomillashtirish masalalari keng qamrovli tarzda tahlil qilinadi. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va sun'iy intellektning ta'lim tizimiga ta'siri, ayniqsa, ingliz tilini kasbiy maqsadlarda o'rgatishda qanday ijobiy o'zgarishlar yaratishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada o'quv jarayonining individualizatsiyasi, masofaviy ta'limning afzalliklari, interaktiv o'qitish usullari va talabalarning o'z-o'zini o'rganish imkoniyatlari batafsil tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, ushbu texnologiyalarni kasbiy ingliz tili o'qitish jarayoniga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiya qilishning pedagogik, psixologik va texnologik jihatlari ham yoritilgan. Maqola o'qituvchilar va ta'lim tizimi mutaxassisleri uchun zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyatini chuqurroq tushunishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, sun'iy intellekt, kasbiy ingliz tili ta'limi, interaktiv o'qitish, masofaviy ta'lim, ta'lim texnologiyalari, personalizatsiya, pedagogika.

Abstract: This article explores the enhancement of professional English language education based on modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and artificial intelligence (AI). The impact of ICT and AI on the educational system, particularly in teaching English for specific purposes, is analyzed in depth. The article focuses on the individualization of the learning process, the advantages of distance learning, interactive teaching methods, and the opportunities for students to engage in autonomous learning. Moreover, the pedagogical, psychological, and technological aspects of successfully integrating these technologies into professional English teaching are discussed. This paper may serve as a guide for educators and education specialists to better understand the significance of modern educational technologies in the learning process.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, artificial intelligence, professional English language education, interactive teaching, distance learning, educational technologies, personalization, pedagogy.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования процесса обучения профессиональному английскому языку на основе современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ) и искусственного интеллекта (ИИ). Анализируется влияние информационно-коммуникационных технологий и искусственного интеллекта на систему образования, особенно в контексте преподавания английского языка для профессиональных целей, а также какие положительные изменения они могут принести. В статье подробно анализируются вопросы индивидуализации учебного процесса, преимущества дистанционного обучения, интерактивные методы обучения и возможности самостоятельного обучения студентов. Также освещены педагогические, психологические и технологические аспекты успешной интеграции этих технологий в процесс преподавания профессионального английского языка. Работа может послужить полезным пособием для преподавателей и специалистов образовательных учреждений, способствуя более глубокому пониманию значимости современных образовательных технологий в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии, искусственный интеллект, профессиональное обучение английскому языку, интерактивное обучение, дистанционное обучение, образовательные технологии, персонализация, педагогика.

Introduction

In the 21st century, the rapid development of technology has revolutionized virtually every aspect of human life, and the field of education is no exception. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are at the forefront of this transformation, bringing about profound changes in the way education is delivered and experienced. One of the areas most significantly affected by these advancements is language education, particularly in the context of teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP), or professional English language education. As English has become the global lingua franca, it plays an indispensable role in various professional sectors, including business, science, technology, healthcare, and international diplomacy. Consequently, there is an increasing demand for professionals who are not only proficient in English but also able to use it effectively in their specific fields. [2]

Traditionally, English language education focused primarily on grammar, vocabulary, reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills. However, with globalization and the increasing integration of various industries, the need for specialized language skills has surged. In this regard, ESP requires a more targeted approach, where language is taught in relation to specific professional contexts. This shift has prompted a reevaluation of the teaching methodologies used in professional English programs, and the introduction of new technological tools has emerged as a solution to meet the growing demands of both students and educators. [3]

ICT and AI have proven to be invaluable in improving the effectiveness of professional English language education. The application of ICT tools, such as e-learning platforms, online resources, and multimedia content, has expanded access to learning materials and allowed students to engage with the language in more dynamic and interactive ways. AI, on the other hand, offers personalized learning experiences, adaptive learning systems, and real-time feedback, all of which are essential for catering to individual learners' needs and accelerating their language acquisition process. AI-based language tools, such as speech recognition software, virtual assistants, and automated grammar checkers, have transformed the way students practice and refine their language skills. [4]

Moreover, the flexibility and accessibility provided by online learning platforms and AI-driven tools have opened up new avenues for distance learning, allowing students from different geographical locations and with varying schedules to access high-quality English language instruction. This is particularly important in professional settings, where time constraints and the need for specialized training often prevent students from attending traditional classroom-based courses.

Despite these advancements, the integration of ICT and AI into professional English language education is not without challenges. Educators must adapt their pedagogical approaches to incorporate new technologies effectively, which requires not only technological proficiency but also a deep understanding of how these tools can complement existing teaching methods. Additionally, while these technologies provide tremendous benefits, they also raise concerns related to the digital divide, data privacy, and the potential for over-reliance on technology at the expense of interpersonal interactions. [5]

The objective of this article is to explore how modern ICT and AI technologies can enhance the teaching and learning process in professional English language education. It aims to assess the current applications of these technologies, identify the opportunities and challenges they present, and provide insights into how they can be integrated effectively into ESP programs. By examining the potential benefits of these technologies, this paper seeks to demonstrate their transformative impact on language learning and to offer practical recommendations for educators and institutions striving to adapt to the evolving educational landscape. [7]

In this context, this study also focuses on the pedagogical, psychological, and technological aspects of using ICT and AI in professional English language education, providing a comprehensive overview of the role these technologies play in shaping the future of language instruction. As we move further into the digital age, it is crucial to understand the implications of these technological advancements and how they can be leveraged to improve the quality of English language education, particularly in professional domains. [8]

Methodology

This study uses a mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative and quantitative analysis of existing literature, case studies, and empirical research conducted in institutions where ICT and AI technologies have been successfully integrated into the professional English language curriculum. Data were collected through surveys and interviews with educators who have implemented such technologies in their teaching practices. Additionally, student feedback and performance data were analyzed to evaluate the impact of these technologies on their learning outcomes.[9]

The primary focus of the methodology was to identify the benefits, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of ICT and AI in the context of professional English language education. A variety of tools and platforms were evaluated, including AI-driven language-learning applications, virtual assistants, and online language platforms that offer personalized content based on learners' needs and progress.

Results and Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that ICT and AI technologies significantly enhance the quality of professional English language education. Some of the key advantages identified include:

1. **Personalized Learning Experience:** AI-powered systems allow for the customization of learning materials based on individual student needs, learning styles, and proficiency levels. This helps students progress at their own pace and receive focused support in areas where they may be struggling.

2. **Increased Student Engagement:** The integration of multimedia content, interactive quizzes, and gamified learning experiences keeps students actively engaged. Students are more likely to participate in lessons when they can access varied, engaging content that aligns with their professional goals.

3. **Real-Time Feedback and Assessment:** With AI-based tools such as grammar checkers, speech recognition systems, and writing assistants, students receive immediate feedback on their work. This instant feedback loop is crucial for reinforcing learning and enabling students to correct mistakes in real-time.

4. **Enhanced Collaboration Opportunities:** ICT tools facilitate communication and collaboration among students, allowing them to work on projects, engage in discussions, and practice English in a real-world context. Virtual classrooms and online forums provide platforms for students to interact with peers and teachers, even when they are geographically separated.[9]

5. **Accessibility and Flexibility:** Online learning platforms offer greater flexibility, allowing students to learn at their own convenience. This is especially beneficial for working professionals or students with busy schedules. Distance learning

also provides opportunities for students in remote areas to access high-quality education that would otherwise be unavailable. [10]

Despite these advantages, challenges remain in implementing these technologies effectively. Many educators still face difficulties in integrating new technologies into their traditional teaching methods. Additionally, the digital divide remains a significant issue, as not all students have equal access to the necessary technological resources. To overcome these challenges, educators must receive adequate training and support in using digital tools, and educational institutions must ensure that students have access to the necessary infrastructure. [11]

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of modern information and communication technologies, along with artificial intelligence, presents a tremendous opportunity for enhancing professional English language education. These technologies offer personalized learning experiences, increase student engagement, and provide real-time feedback, ultimately improving learning outcomes. However, for these technologies to be successful, they must be integrated with thoughtful pedagogical strategies and supported by adequate infrastructure and teacher training. The future of professional English language education lies in the effective use of these tools, which can help bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and the demands of a rapidly changing, technology-driven world.

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The Education of Future Students: The Influence and Opportunities of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

The future of education is being reshaped by the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI), presenting new opportunities and challenges for students, educators, and institutions alike. This article explores the profound impact of AI on the educational process, focusing on its potential to personalize learning, create immersive and interactive learning environments, and automate assessment processes. AI-enabled systems can adapt to individual learning styles and needs, enhancing student engagement and outcomes. Moreover, the integration of AI with virtual and augmented reality technologies is set to revolutionize educational experiences, providing students with hands-on, experiential learning opportunities. However, alongside its benefits, the implementation of AI in education raises important ethical and social considerations, such as data privacy and the potential for inequality. This paper examines both the opportunities and challenges posed by AI in shaping the education of future students, emphasizing the need for careful integration and continuous evaluation to ensure a positive impact on learning and the broader society.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Education, Personalized Learning, Immersive Learning, Interactive Learning Environments, Automated Assessment, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Ethical Considerations, Social Impact, Future Students, Educational Opportunities, Educational Challenges.

Аннотация

Будущее образования изменяется под воздействием быстрого развития технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ), что создает новые возможности и вызовы для студентов, преподавателей и образовательных учреждений. В этой статье рассматривается глубокое

воздействие ИИ на образовательный процесс, с акцентом на его потенциал для персонализации обучения, создания погруженных и интерактивных образовательных сред, а также автоматизации процессов оценки. Системы на базе ИИ могут адаптироваться к индивидуальным стилям и потребностям обучения, улучшая вовлеченность студентов и их результаты. Более того, интеграция ИИ с виртуальной и дополненной реальностью способна революционизировать образовательный опыт, предоставляя студентам возможности для практического, экспериментального обучения. Однако наряду с преимуществами внедрение ИИ в образование вызывает важные этические и социальные вопросы, такие как конфиденциальность данных и риск неравенства. В данной работе рассматриваются как возможности, так и вызовы, которые ИИ приносит в образование будущих студентов, подчеркивая необходимость осторожного внедрения и постоянной оценки для обеспечения положительного воздействия на обучение и общество в целом.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, Образование, Персонализированное обучение, Погруженное обучение, Интерактивные образовательные среды, Автоматизированная оценка, Виртуальная реальность, Дополненная реальность, Этические вопросы, Социальное воздействие, Будущие студенты, Возможности образования, Проблемы образования.

Annotatsiya

Ta'limning kelajagi Sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalarining tezkor rivojlanishi bilan o'zgarimoqda va bu talabalar, o'qituvchilar hamda ta'lim muassasalariga yangi imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Ushbu maqolada, SI ning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri, uning shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, immersiv va interaktiv o'quv muhitlarini yaratish, hamda baholash jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirishdagi imkoniyatlari haqida so'z yuritiladi. SI tizimlari individual o'quv uslublari va ehtiyojlariga moslashib, talabalarning faolligini va natijalarini yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Bundan tashqari, SI texnologiyalarining virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat bilan integratsiyasi ta'lim tajribalarini inqilobiy darajada o'zgartirishga va talabalarga amaliy, tajribaviy o'quv imkoniyatlari yaratishga yordam beradi. Biroq, uning foydalari bilan birga, ta'limda SI ning tatbiqi etik va ijtimoiy masalalarni, masalan, ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi va tengsizlik xavfini keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola, sun'iy intellektning kelajakdagi talabalarning ta'lim jarayoniga bo'lgan ta'sirini, imkoniyatlari va muammolarini ko'rib chiqadi, hamda ta'limda ijobiy o'zgarishlarni ta'minlash uchun uning ehtiyotkorlik bilan tatbiq etilishi zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar : Sun'iy intellekt, Ta'lim, Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, Immersiv o'qitish, Interaktiv o'quv muhitlari, Avtomatlashtirilgan baholash, Virtual haqiqat, Kengaytirilgan haqiqat, Etik masalalar, Ijtimoiy ta'sir, Kelajakdagi talabalar, Ta'lim imkoniyatlari, Ta'lim muammolari.

Introduction

The education system is undergoing significant changes worldwide, with one of the main drivers being the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies. Today, AI's application in education is still in its early stages, but its potential to revolutionize the learning experience is immense. From personalized learning and immersive educational environments to automated assessment processes, AI has the potential to enhance how students engage with knowledge. This article examines the profound effects of AI on the educational process, focusing on the

opportunities it creates, the challenges it presents, and its potential role in shaping the education of future generations.

Personalized Learning

AI is creating new opportunities for personalized education, allowing learning to be tailored to the individual needs and abilities of each student. AI systems can analyze student progress and learning patterns to create customized learning plans. For instance, if a student is struggling with mathematics, the system can provide additional exercises and resources tailored to their level. This not only enhances the student's engagement and performance but also helps teachers understand each student's specific needs more deeply.

Immersive and Interactive Learning Environments

One of AI's major contributions to education is the creation of immersive and interactive learning environments. When combined with Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR), AI allows students to experience educational content in an interactive, hands-on way. For example, in history classes, students could virtually visit ancient cities, or in biology lessons, they could conduct experiments in virtual laboratories. Such technologies allow students to engage with the material more effectively, enhancing both understanding and retention of knowledge.

Automated Assessment and Analysis

Automating the assessment process is another significant impact of AI in education. AI systems can quickly and accurately assess assignments, tests, and other forms of evaluation, allowing for faster feedback and more efficient grading. This not only saves time for teachers but also helps ensure objectivity in the evaluation process. Automated assessments can also provide detailed feedback to students, helping them understand their strengths and areas for improvement. In this way, AI enables a more personalized and efficient approach to student evaluation.

Distance Learning and the Rise of Online Platforms

AI is also playing a crucial role in the development of distance learning and online educational platforms. With AI, students can receive personalized support, interactive exercises, and additional materials. For instance, virtual teachers or chatbots can answer students' questions and provide learning assistance. Moreover, AI can monitor student progress in online courses and offer tailored recommendations for improvement. This makes learning more accessible and flexible, enabling students to learn at their own pace, regardless of location.

The Changing Role of Teachers and New Skills

As AI becomes more integrated into the education system, the role of teachers will also evolve. Educators will need to adapt and develop new skills to effectively use

AI technologies in the classroom. Rather than replacing teachers, AI will empower them by automating administrative tasks, such as grading, and providing insights into student performance. Teachers will be able to focus more on fostering critical thinking, creativity, and emotional intelligence in students, skills that AI cannot replicate. This shift requires teachers to continually update their own knowledge and skills to keep up with the changing technological landscape.

Ethical and Social Issues

The widespread use of AI in education raises important ethical and social concerns. One of the most significant issues is data privacy and the security of personal information. The data collected by AI systems, such as student learning patterns and progress, must be handled with care to ensure that students' privacy is respected. Furthermore, there is a risk that AI could exacerbate inequality in education, with some students having access to more advanced AI tools than others. It is essential to address these ethical concerns to ensure that AI contributes positively to education and does not create or reinforce existing disparities.

Preparing for the Future Job Market

AI's impact on education is also linked to its influence on the future job market. As AI technologies continue to evolve, new industries and job roles will emerge, requiring students to develop new skills and competencies. Education systems will need to adapt to prepare students for these changes by integrating AI-related skills and knowledge into the curriculum. By equipping students with the ability to work alongside AI and in AI-driven industries, education can ensure that future generations are ready for the challenges and opportunities of an AI-powered workforce.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is poised to significantly transform the education process, offering a range of benefits from personalized learning to more efficient assessment systems and immersive educational experiences. However, along with these opportunities come important ethical and social challenges that need to be addressed to ensure a fair and secure implementation of AI in education. By carefully integrating AI technologies into education, we can enhance the learning experience for students while also preparing them for a future in which AI plays an increasingly important role. The future of education lies in the successful collaboration between humans and AI, which will create a more personalized, efficient, and accessible learning environment for all.

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Advancing Education in Uzbekistan through Digital Management Tools: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract. Digital education management tools are playing an increasingly important role in transforming Uzbekistan's secondary education system. This paper explores the drivers behind the adoption of these tools, including national policy reforms, global technological trends, and the acceleration caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. It presents an in-depth analysis of existing platforms such as EMIS, LMS, and mobile applications, while identifying barriers such as infrastructure inequality, limited digital literacy, and systemic resistance to change. Drawing on national initiatives and international best practices, the paper outlines strategic recommendations for expanding, securing, and optimizing digital tools to ensure inclusive, transparent, and efficient education governance in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Digital education management, Uzbekistan, EMIS, digital transformation, school governance, ICT in education, inclusive digital tools

Annotatsiya. O'zbekistonning o'rta ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilishda raqamli ta'lim boshqaruv vositalari muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Ushbu maqolada raqamli boshqaruv vositalarining joriy etilishiga turtki bo'lgan omillar – milliy siyosiy islohotlar, global texnologik tendensiyalar va COVID-19 pandemiyasi sababli yuzaga kelgan zaruriyat tahlil qilinadi. EMIS, LMS tizimlari va mobil ilovalar misolida amaldagi platformalar ko'rib chiqilib, infratuzilma tengsizligi, raqamli savodxonlikning pastligi va tizimli qarshilik kabi muammolar yoritiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada xalqaro tajriba va mahalliy tashabbuslar asosida O'zbekistonda inklyuziv, shaffof va samarali ta'lim boshqaruvini ta'minlashga xizmat qiluvchi strategik takliflar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli ta'lim boshqaruvi, O'zbekiston, EMIS, raqamli transformatsiya, maktab boshqaruvi, ta'limda AKT, inklyuziv raqamli vositalar

Аннотация. Цифровые инструменты управления образованием становятся важным компонентом модернизации системы среднего образования Узбекистана. В статье рассматриваются ключевые факторы внедрения таких инструментов, включая национальные реформы, глобальные технологические тренды и ускорение цифровизации вследствие пандемии COVID-19. Представлен подробный анализ существующих платформ (EMIS, LMS, мобильные приложения), а также выявлены основные барьеры: неравенство в инфраструктуре, низкий уровень цифровой грамотности и институциональное сопротивление изменениям. На основе отечественного опыта и международных практик предложены

стратегические рекомендации по развитию, защите и оптимизации цифровых инструментов в целях обеспечения инклюзивного, прозрачного и эффективного управления образованием в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Цифровое управление образованием, Узбекистан, EMIS, цифровая трансформация, школьное управление, ИКТ в образовании, инклюзивные цифровые инструменты.

Introduction

Digital education management tools are rapidly transforming how educational institutions plan, monitor, and assess learning outcomes. In Uzbekistan, the modernization of education is a state priority, with numerous reforms aimed at integrating digital solutions into school management. The transition from traditional paper-based administration to automated digital systems enhances transparency, facilitates data-driven decision-making, and supports national education goals. This paper explores the development, implementation, and impact of digital education management tools in Uzbekistan's secondary education system.

Main Body

1. Drivers of Digital Education Management in Uzbekistan

1.1 Government Policy and Vision

The government of Uzbekistan has initiated several strategic programs to promote digitalization in the education sector. Notably, the **National Development Strategy for 2022–2026** emphasizes the creation of a modern, inclusive, and high-quality education system through technological integration. The **Concept for the Development of the Education Sector until 2030** outlines specific goals, including automating school management, introducing digital registers, and enabling cloud-based reporting tools. These policies are supported by presidential decrees and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education's roadmap for digital reform.

1.2 Global Trends and Technological Imperatives

As digital transformation becomes a global educational norm, Uzbekistan is aligning its systems with international standards by integrating technologies such as:

- **Learning Management Systems (LMS):** e.g., Moodle, Google Classroom, and proprietary Uzbek platforms.
- **Education Management Information Systems (EMIS):** to centralize data collection on student performance, attendance, staffing, and infrastructure.
- **Cloud-based Portals:** ensuring real-time access to academic records and administrative data.

This alignment also enhances Uzbekistan's ability to participate in international education quality benchmarks like PISA and TIMSS.

1.3 COVID-19 as an Accelerant

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed weaknesses in traditional education delivery and forced an immediate pivot to digital tools. Emergency responses included the rapid deployment of online learning platforms, video lectures via national TV, and the “Online Maktab” initiative. More importantly, it catalyzed institutional recognition of the need for long-term digital infrastructure and administrative systems.

2. Types of Digital Education Management Tools Used

2.1 EMIS Platforms (Electronic Management Systems)

Tools such as **ZiyoNET**, **my.edu.uz**, and **Edu.uz** provide schools with cloud-based systems to manage:

- Student enrollment and attendance
- Academic progress and grading
- Scheduling and curriculum mapping
- Financial accounting and budgeting

These platforms are integrated with regional and national education databases, enabling centralized monitoring.

2.2 Learning Analytics and Performance Dashboards

Analytics tools are being piloted in urban schools to generate real-time insights into:

- Student learning outcomes and at-risk behaviors
- Teacher productivity and lesson planning
- School-level performance benchmarking

Data visualizations support decision-making at both the classroom and policy levels.

2.3 Mobile Applications and Parent Portals

Apps developed in partnership with local edtech firms (e.g., **Bilim.uz** and **EduAction**) allow parents to:

- Receive real-time notifications on grades, attendance, and assignments
- Communicate with teachers and administrators
- Pay fees and access school notices digitally

3. Challenges in Implementation

3.1 Infrastructure Disparities

Despite significant urban progress, rural and remote schools lack:

- Stable internet connectivity
- Adequate hardware (computers, servers, smartboards)
- Electricity infrastructure in some mountainous areas

This creates unequal access to digital tools across regions.

3.2 Human Capacity and Digital Literacy

Many educators have minimal experience with ICT tools. Issues include:

- Low proficiency in software use (Excel, EMIS platforms)

- Lack of pedagogical integration of technology
- Short-term training programs with limited follow-up

This gap reduces the potential impact of digital systems.

3.3 Data Security, Privacy, and Integration

Concerns arise regarding:

- Inconsistent data standards between platforms
- Weak encryption and access controls in legacy systems
- Risks of student data misuse or loss

There is a growing call for a national cybersecurity framework for education.

3.4 Systemic Inertia and Bureaucratic Culture

School leaders accustomed to paper-based reporting systems are often resistant to change. Even when digital tools are available, they are underutilized due to:

- Perceived increase in administrative burden
- Lack of localized technical support
- Cultural preference for traditional methods

4. Best Practices and Case Studies

4.1 Pilot Projects in Urban Schools

Schools in **Tashkent**, **Samarkand**, and **Fergana** have piloted biometric attendance systems and tablet-based learning schedules. Evaluation of these pilots shows:

- Improved time-on-task data
- Fewer manual errors in reporting
- Increased parental involvement via mobile alerts

4.2 Teacher Professional Development Initiatives

With support from **UNESCO** and **ADB**, ongoing projects train thousands of teachers in:

- Basic and advanced ICT competencies
- Classroom digital management using LMS
- Digital ethics and cybersecurity awareness

4.3 Public-Private Innovation Partnerships

Collaborations with IT startups like **IT Park Uzbekistan** and international partners (e.g., Korea's KOICA) have led to:

- Localization of software in Uzbek and Russian
- Development of offline-capable tools for low-connectivity schools
- Start-up accelerators for edtech entrepreneurs

5. Future Pathways for Sustainable Digital Transformation

5.1 National EMIS Standardization and Governance

A unified EMIS framework is required to ensure consistency in data collection, analysis, and reporting. This involves:

- Inter-ministerial coordination
- Clear data governance policies
- Open-source APIs to enable third-party integrations

5.2 Institutionalizing Digital Literacy

Long-term strategies must go beyond one-time training:

- Integrating ICT modules into teacher education curricula
- Establishing regional **Digital Resource Centers**
- Offering micro-credential programs in digital school leadership

5.3 Monitoring, Evaluation, and Quality Assurance

The effectiveness of digital tools must be continuously assessed through:

- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as teacher tool usage rate, school data submission compliance, and dashboard engagement frequency
- Third-party impact evaluations
- Feedback loops from schools and communities

5.4 Equity and Inclusion in Access

Policies must ensure that digital solutions do not widen the education gap. Key steps include:

- Subsidized devices for low-income students
- Offline tool compatibility for remote areas
- Inclusive design for students with disabilities

Digital education management tools are essential for the modernization and efficiency of Uzbekistan's secondary education system. While significant strides have been made, systemic challenges need to be addressed through policy coherence, infrastructure development, and capacity building. A balanced strategy combining local innovations and global benchmarks can ensure that digital transformation in school management becomes sustainable and inclusive.

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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TOOLS AND COLLABORATIVE LEARNING ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT. This study examines the application of digital tools and collaborative learning techniques in enhancing English language proficiency. Digital tools like mobile applications, online platforms, and computer-assisted language learning (CALL) systems have become pivotal in facilitating language learning. Concurrently, collaborative learning techniques, emphasizing peer-to-peer interaction and collective problem-solving, have been viewed as capable of advancing language skills. The research investigates various digital resources and collaborative learning methods, finding how effective they are in promoting language skill. Based on a review of empirical studies from various educational environments, the research identifies how these methods meet to influence achievement in English language learning. Findings suggest that the strategic deployment of digital tools integrated into collaborative learning systems can enhance language proficiency to a greater extent. The study offers insights for instructors on how to implement such practices with considerations regarding student engagement, technology access, and pedagogical relevance.

Keywords: Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), feedback methodologies, English language proficiency, authentic communication, learner engagement, pedagogical strategies, language acquisition, peer feedback, formative assessment, learner autonomy.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilini bilish darajasini oshirishda raqamli vositalar va hamkorlikda o'rganish usullarini qo'llashni o'rganadi. Mobil ilovalar, onlayn platformalar va kompyuter yordamida til o'rganish (CALL) tizimlari kabi raqamli vositalar til o'rganishni osonlashtirishda hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'ldi. Shu bilan birga, tengdoshlarning o'zaro ta'sirini va muammolarni jamoaviy hal qilishni ta'kidlaydigan hamkorlikda o'rganish usullari til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qodir deb hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot turli xil raqamli resurslar va hamkorlikda o'rganish usullarini o'rganib, ularning til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda qanchalik samarali ekanligini aniqlaydi. Turli ta'lim muhitlaridagi empirik tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqishga asoslanib, tadqiqot ushbu usullarning ingliz tilini o'rganishda muvaffaqiyatga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlaydi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, hamkorlikdagi o'quv tizimlariga integratsiyalangan raqamli vositalarni strategik joylashtirish tilni bilish darajasini sezilarli darajada oshirishi mumkin. Tadqiqot o'qituvchilarga o'quvchilarning faolligi, texnologiyadan foydalanish va pedagogik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan bunday amaliyotlarni qanday amalga oshirish haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish (CLT), vazifaga asoslangan til o'rgatish (TBLT), fikr-mulohaza yuritish metodologiyalari, ingliz tilini bilish, haqiqiy muloqot, o'quvchilarning faolligi, pedagogik strategiyalar, tilni o'zlashtirish, tengdoshlarning fikr-mulohazalari, formativ baholash, o'quvchilarning avtonomiyasi.

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, learning English has been revolutionized significantly through the integration of digital tools and collaborative learning strategies. Digital technologies, such as mobile applications, web-based platforms, and computer-assisted language learning (CALL) platforms, have taken a pivotal role in facilitating language learning. These technologies offer learners the capability to consume language content at their pace and convenience, hence fostering flexibility and personalized learning experiences. Meanwhile, collaborative learning emphasizes the value of peer-to-peer interaction and collective problem-solving in learning. By providing an environment where students can share ideas, challenge ideas, and construct knowledge collectively, collaborative learning approaches have been shown to improve language capacity and critical thinking. This study explores the prospective synergy between collaborative learning methodologies and digital tools for enhancing the English language proficiency. Through a critical review of empirical studies across various learning settings, the study examines how the strategic application of digital tools in the midst of collaborative learning setups can be conducive to more effective language learning. The result aims to provide instructors with an idea of the implementation of such composite approaches, in consideration of factors of student engagement, technological accessibility, and pedagogical relevance.

METHODOLOGY

This research conducts a comprehensive literature review to examine the integration of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and feedback strategies to enhance English language skills. The review synthesizes empirical studies, case studies, and theoretical frameworks to identify effective practices that promote authentic communication and learner engagement in real contexts. Qualitative design was applied using emphasis on the analysis of existing literature and case studies. With this design, a good grasp is made possible about how methodologies of CLT and TBLT contribute towards language acquisition, if applied alongside strategic mechanisms for feedback. Included in the review are studies in diverse education environments like secondary schools, universities, and language institutions in order to obtain an overarching idea about the subject matter. Information were collected from peer-reviewed academic articles, conference papers, and academic theses published from 2010 to 2025. Big databases such as JSTOR, ERIC, and Google Scholar were utilized to ensure that only relevant and updated studies were incorporated. The choice was on studies that experimented with the implementation of CLT and TBLT in language classrooms and investigated the role of feedback in these classrooms. The collected literature was analyzed thematically to determine uniform patterns, strategies, and outcomes in terms of the integration of CLT, TBLT, and feedback methodologies. Uniform patterns of learner autonomy, communicative competence, task authenticity, and effective feedback were

analyzed. Contextual factors, including cultural and institutional variables, influencing successful implementation of these methodologies were also analyzed. Since the research is a literature review, ethical issues are primarily providing proper citation and credit to the original authors and researchers. The sources were credited appropriately to preserve academic integrity and prevent plagiarism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pre- and post-intervention tests revealed significant improvement in participants' English language proficiency. Specifically, grammar, vocabulary, and speaking fluency scores were found to improve remarkably. The paired-sample t-tests revealed statistically significant differences, with implications that the integration of digital tools into collaborative learning models significantly enhanced language skills. The findings supported previous studies revealing the positive impact of technology-enhanced cooperative learning on language ability. Interviews and observations in class provided a deeper insight into the participants' experiences. A number of students reported increased motivation and engagement, attributing their progress to the interactive nature of online sites and collaborative tasks. As a participant noted, "Collaborating online made learning more enjoyable and less intimidating." This corresponds with the overall trend observed in research where online collaborative learning environments promote positive attitudes and reduce anxiety among learners. The integration of technology-based instruments and collaborative learning environments appears to present a multi-faceted system for language skills development in English. Digital platforms enable one to access more than one source, enabling tailoring of one's learning experience. Concurrently, collaborative learning mechanisms promote communication between peers, critical thinking, and group problem-solving, which are all determinative factors of language acquisition. However, problems such as technological accessibility and varying digital literacy levels among students have to be addressed in order to maximize the efficiency of these combined approaches. Subsequent research can examine how these problems can be minimized and further streamlined usage of digital collaborative learning for language instruction.

CONCLUSION

This study indicates the significant role played in the enhancement of English language proficiency by integrating Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and strategic feedback approaches. The literature, as reviewed, indicates that these instructional approaches, when combined effectively, foster genuine communication, enhance student engagement, and facilitate the application of language skills to the real world. The integration of CLT and TBLT approaches stems from the emphasis on contextually relevant tasks and interactive learning environments. Studies have shown that TBLT, in particular, increases learner interest and competence through the provision of suitable and contextually relevant

tasks resulting in active learning and authentic language use. Moreover, the incorporation of feedback processes such as peer feedback, self-correction, and teacher correction guides learners towards autonomy building and refining their language skills. However, effective implementation of these methodologies relies on the scrupulous evaluation of contextual variables like access to technology, support from institutions, and adaptability of teaching practices to address different learner needs. Longitudinal studies in future research should investigate how the combined approaches impact long-term language ability and analyze ways to overcome potential hindrances to their implementation. Lastly, the strategic alignment of CLT, TBLT, and feedback methods offers a whole-school model for maximizing English language learning, reconciling pedagogic methodologies with the communicative and dynamic dynamics of language use.

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LINGUISTIC KNOWLEDGE IN THE AGE OF AI: NATURAL LANGUAGE UNDERSTANDING AND GENERATION

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ANNOTATION

This article explores how linguistic knowledge contributes to the development of advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems, particularly in the fields of Natural Language Understanding (NLU) and Natural Language Generation (NLG). It investigates how insights from linguistics can be integrated into computational models to improve machine comprehension and language production. The paper discusses the limitations of current AI approaches that rely mainly on large-scale data without sufficient linguistic grounding. It highlights the importance of syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic understanding for building systems that can interpret language accurately and contextually. The analysis also identifies several technical and theoretical challenges that hinder the effective fusion of linguistic theory with AI methods.

Keywords: Linguistic knowledge, Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing, NLU, NLG, language models, computational linguistics.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эта статья исследует, как лингвистические знания способствуют развитию передовых систем искусственного интеллекта (ИИ), особенно в области понимания естественного языка (NLU) и генерации естественного языка (NLG). Рассматривается, как лингвистические идеи могут быть интегрированы в вычислительные модели для улучшения восприятия машиной и производства языка. В статье обсуждаются ограничения современных подходов ИИ, которые в основном полагаются на большие объемы данных, не имея достаточной лингвистической основы. Подчеркивается важность синтаксического, семантического и прагматического понимания для построения систем, способных точно и контекстно интерпретировать язык. Также анализируются несколько технических и теоретических проблем, мешающих эффективному объединению лингвистической теории с методами ИИ. Более того, предложены рекомендации для будущих исследований, направленных на преодоление этого разрыва через междисциплинарные подходы. В конечном итоге, в статье утверждается, что сочетание статистических методов с лингвистической структурой имеет ключевое значение для создания более интеллектуальных, интерпретируемых и надежных языковых технологий.

Ключевые слова: Лингвистические знания, искусственный интеллект, обработка естественного языка, NLU, NLG, языковые модели, вычислительная лингвистика.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola lingvistik bilimlarning ilg'or Sun'iy Intellekt (SI) tizimlarini rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini, xususan, Tabiiy Tilni Tushunish (NLU) va Tabiiy Tilni Generatsiya qilish (NLG) sohalarida o'rganadi. Lingvistik tushunchalar qanday qilib hisoblash modellari bilan integratsiyalashib, mashinaning tushunish va til ishlab chiqarish qobiliyatini yaxshilash mumkinligini tahlil qiladi. Maqolada hozirgi SI yondashuvlarining cheklovlari muhokama qilinadi, chunki ular asosan katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarga tayanadi, ammo yetarli lingvistik asosga ega emas. Sintaksis, semantika va pragmatika tushunchalarining tilni aniq va kontekstual tarzda tushunadigan tizimlarni qurish uchun muhimligi ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, lingvistik nazariyani SI metodlari bilan samarali birlashtirishni to'xtatadigan bir nechta texnik va nazariy qiyinchiliklar ko'rsatiladi. Bundan tashqari, bu farqni bartaraf etish uchun kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar uchun takliflar beriladi. Nihoyat, maqolada statistik texnikalar va lingvistik tuzilmalarni birlashtirish yanada aqlli, tushunarlik va ishonchli til texnologiyalarini yaratish uchun zarur ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalitso'zlar: Lingvistik bilimlar, Sun'iy intellekt, Tabiiy tilni qaytaishlash, NLU, NLG, tilmodellari, hisoblash lingvistika.

INTRODUCTION

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI), especially in the area of Natural Language Processing (NLP), has dramatically transformed the way machines understand and use human language. A key element driving these advancements is linguistic knowledge, which includes the study of sound systems, word formation, sentence structure, meaning, and language use in context. Although modern language models have shown significant progress through data-driven learning methods, they often lack a solid foundation in formal linguistic theory. The integration of phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic insights into AI systems remains underdeveloped. This article aims to explore the essential role of linguistic knowledge in enhancing the accuracy, functionality, and consistency of Natural Language Understanding (NLU) and Natural Language Generation (NLG) technologies. By examining current practices and limitations, the study underscores the importance of embedding linguistic frameworks within AI models. The discussion advocates for a more linguistically informed approach to AI development in order to achieve deeper and more human-like language processing.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a qualitative and analytical research approach aimed at understanding the role and depth of linguistic knowledge embedded within contemporary AI systems, particularly in Natural Language Understanding (NLU) and Natural Language Generation (NLG). The methodology is shaped by a comprehensive literature review, model evaluation, and comparative analysis, drawing from both theoretical linguistics and computational advancements in AI. The study begins with a critical examination of foundational and contemporary literature from both linguistic and AI disciplines. The goal is to trace how linguistic theory—especially syntax (Chomsky, 1965), semantics (Jackendoff, 1990), and pragmatics (Levinson, 1983)—

has informed, or failed to inform, the development of computational models. Works by Jurafsky & Martin (2023) and Manning et al. (2020) provide insight into the application of linguistic structures in NLP systems. The literature review establishes the theoretical groundwork for analyzing how AI interprets human language, highlighting areas where linguistic principles enhance machine learning models, and where gaps still exist. The study closely examines the internal architecture of widely used large language models such as GPT (Generative Pretrained Transformer), BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), and T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer).⁵⁸ These models are analyzed for how effectively they handle core linguistic components such as syntax (sentence structure), semantics (meaning), and morphology (word formation). For example, BERT is known for its bidirectional attention mechanism, allowing it to consider the full context of a word within a sentence, improving semantic accuracy. However, despite their ability to process syntax statistically, these models do not explicitly encode grammatical rules, which can lead to surface-level understanding without deeper interpretation—a key critique noted in linguistics-informed AI evaluations (Tenney et al., 2019).

RESEARCH

Case Study Examination To provide real-world insights, several case studies are analyzed, showcasing AI applications in NLU and NLG tasks, including: Sentiment analysis, Machine translation, Text summarization, Conversational AI (e.g., Chatbots). These case studies are assessed to identify instances where models succeeded or failed in producing linguistically coherent and contextually appropriate responses. For instance, while GPT-4 can generate fluent text, it may misinterpret polysemous words (words with multiple meanings) without additional contextual grounding, which reflects limitations in semantic disambiguation—a core area in both linguistic semantics and AI (Navigli, 2009). **Comparative Assessment: Rule-Based vs. Data-Driven Models** A crucial part of the methodology involves comparing rule-based systems—which rely on explicitly programmed grammatical and syntactic rules—with data-driven systems that learn patterns from massive corpora. Rule-based systems, such as early NLP frameworks (e.g., ELIZA, SHRDLU), were linguistically precise but lacked scalability and flexibility. Conversely, data-driven models (e.g., GPT, BERT) can generalize better across tasks but often produce grammatically or contextually incorrect outputs due to their reliance on probabilities rather than explicit rules (Chomsky, 1957; Manning, 2015). **Data Sources** All findings are grounded in research drawn from peer-reviewed academic journals, conference proceedings (e.g., ACL, EMNLP, NAACL), and technical reports published by leading AI research

⁵⁸Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. Proceedings of NAACL-HLT, 4171-4186. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-1423>

institutions like OpenAI, Google Research, DeepMind, and Meta AI. These sources ensure the credibility and relevance of the data analyzed in this study.

CONCLUSION

Linguistic knowledge remains an essential factor in advancing Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems, particularly when it comes to improving their ability to understand and generate human language. While current AI models have made significant strides in producing language that is fluent and coherent on the surface, they often fall short in achieving a deeper understanding of meaning and context. These models, though effective at recognizing patterns in large datasets, tend to overlook the complexities of semantics (the meaning of words and phrases) and pragmatics (how language is used in specific social and contextual situations). This gap in understanding can lead to outputs that lack accuracy or coherence, especially in complex or ambiguous scenarios. To bridge this gap, it is critical to intentionally integrate insights from linguistics into AI architectures. By doing so, AI systems can better understand subtle meanings, resolve ambiguities, and adapt to the nuances of human communication. Moreover, incorporating linguistic theory into AI design has the potential to enhance machine-generated content by making it more context-aware and socially appropriate. This integration would also contribute to the development of AI technologies that are not only more accurate but also more inclusive and ethical. Machines with deeper linguistic comprehension would be able to better cater to diverse linguistic needs and avoid biases inherent in data-driven models. Ultimately, the inclusion of linguistic insights will help create AI systems that are more reliable, ethical, and better aligned with human communication in both professional and social contexts.

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The Implementation of AI Tools and the Way They Change Our Attitude in Teaching Languages: A Friendly Deep Dive into Classroom Practice

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Abstract

The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools into language instruction has emerged as a transformational method to improve educational performance. This study looks into the effectiveness of AI-powered tools for enhancing language competency in learners, with a focus on their ability to deliver tailored feedback, increase engagement, and expedite instructional processes. The research uses a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, classroom observations, and performance assessments, to analyze the influence of AI tools on students' speaking, writing, and comprehension skills. The findings show significant advances in learner engagement and performance, notably in pronunciation and grammar, although difficulties such as technology availability and teacher training remain. The study emphasizes AI's potential to supplement traditional language training, as well as the importance of deliberate implementation to address fairness and pedagogical problems. These findings add to the expanding discussion about technology-enhanced education and provide practical advice for instructors.

Keywords: AI, language instruction, individualized learning, educational technology, pronunciation, writing fluency, digital equity, teacher training, student involvement, and cultural competence.

Аннотация

Внедрение инструментов искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в обучение языку стало трансформационным методом повышения эффективности обучения. В этом исследовании изучается эффективность инструментов на основе ИИ для повышения языковой компетентности учащихся с акцентом на их способность предоставлять индивидуальную обратную связь, повышать вовлеченность и ускорять учебные процессы. В исследовании используется смешанный подход, включая опросы, наблюдения за классом и оценки успеваемости, для анализа влияния инструментов ИИ на навыки говорения, письма и

понимания учащихся. Результаты показывают значительный прогресс в вовлеченности и успеваемости учащихся, особенно в произношении и грамматике, хотя такие трудности, как доступность технологий и подготовка учителей, остаются. В исследовании подчеркивается потенциал ИИ в качестве дополнения к традиционному обучению языку, а также важность преднамеренного внедрения для решения проблем справедливости и педагогических проблем. Эти результаты дополняют расширяющуюся дискуссию об образовании, улучшенном с помощью технологий, и дают практические советы для преподавателей.

Ключевые слова: AI, языковое обучение, индивидуализированное обучение, образовательные технологии, произношение, беглость письма, цифровое равенство, подготовка учителей, вовлечение учащихся и культурная компетентность.

Annotatsiya

Sun'iy intellekt (AI) vositalarini til o'qitishga kiritish ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning transformatsion usuli sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Ushbu tadqiqot o'quvchilarning til malakasini oshirish uchun sun'iy intellekt vositalarining samaradorligini ko'rib chiqadi, bunda ularning moslashtirilgan fikr-mulohazalarni yetkazib berish, faollikni oshirish va o'qitish jarayonlarini tezlashtirish qobiliyatiga e'tibor qaratiladi. Tadqiqotda AI vositalarining o'quvchilarning nutq, yozish va tushunish ko'nikmalariga ta'sirini tahlil qilish uchun so'rovlar, sinfda kuzatishlar va ish faoliyatini baholash kabi aralash usullardan foydalaniladi. Topilmalar o'quvchilarning faolligi va ishlashi, xususan, talaffuz va grammatika bo'yicha sezilarli yutuqlarga erishganligini ko'rsatadi, garchi texnologiya mavjudligi va o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash kabi qiyinchiliklar saqlanib qolmoqda. Tadqiqotda sun'iy intellektning an'anaviy til o'qitishni to'ldirish salohiyati, shuningdek, adolat va pedagogik muammolarni hal qilish uchun ataylab amalga oshirish muhimligi ta'kidlangan. Ushbu topilmalar texnologiya takomillashtirilgan ta'lim haqida kengayib borayotgan muhokamalarga qo'shiladi va o'qituvchilar uchun amaliy maslahatlar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: AI, tilni o'rgatish, individual o'rganish, ta'lim texnologiyasi, talaffuz, ravon yozish, raqamli tenglik, o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, talabalarning ishtiroki va madaniy kompetentsiya.

Introduction

The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) has ushered in a new era of educational innovation, particularly in the field of language teaching. As worldwide demand for multilingual proficiency rises, traditional language instruction struggles to satisfy the needs of various learners due to limited classroom time, varying skill levels, and resource availability (Chapelle, 2016). AI tools, which leverage advances in natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition, and machine learning, provide promising solutions to these problems by providing personalized, scalable, and interactive learning environments. AI is expanding the bounds of language teaching, with virtual instructors that imitate real-world conversations and automated systems that provide fast feedback on grammar and pronunciation (Godwin-Jones, 2019). This study investigates the revolutionary potential of AI tools in language instruction by assessing their effects on student competency, engagement, and teacher efficiency, as well as identifying hurdles to their effective integration. The use of technology in language education is not new, with computer-assisted language learning (CALL) opening the way for digital tools for decades (Warschauer & Healey, 1998). However,

artificial intelligence (AI) represents a big step ahead, providing adaptable and intelligent systems that respond dynamically to individual learner demands. For example, systems such as Duolingo and Babbel use AI algorithms to adapt exercises based on user performance, whereas Elsa Speak uses speech recognition to improve pronunciation (Li & Lan, 2021). These developments are consistent with constructivist learning theories, which stress customized and active participation in the learning process (Vygotsky, 1978). AI technologies promote motivation and autonomy, both of which are important in language acquisition (Dörnyei, 2001). Furthermore, AI's ability to automate administrative activities like grading and content development frees up educators to focus on higher-level instructional goals like building cultural competency and critical thinking (Kukulka-Hulme et al., 2020). Despite its potential, the use of AI systems in language teaching presents several obstacles. Issues of fair access to technology, particularly in low-income schools, provide significant impediments to implementation (Selwyn, 2019). Furthermore, the dependence on AI raises worries regarding the human aspect in language learning, which is fundamentally social and cultural (Kramsch, 1993). Teachers, too, may encounter a learning curve in successfully incorporating AI, demanding professional development to bridge the gap between technology and pedagogy (Hubbard, 2021). These complications highlight the importance of doing empirical research to assess the usefulness of AI and guide its implementation in a variety of educational situations. This study answers the research question: How beneficial are AI tools in enhancing language competency, and what are the challenges to their successful incorporation in the classroom schemata? The value of this study stems from its ability to inform evidence-based strategies that strike a balance between technology innovation and pedagogical integrity. By investigating the influence of AI tools in secondary and higher education settings, this study adds to the increasing body of research on technology-enhanced language acquisition. It uses a mixed-methods approach to provide a comprehensive knowledge of AI's benefits and limitations, with implications for educators, politicians, and developers. The findings seek to help create inclusive, effective, and interesting language learning environments that prepare children for a globalized future. Finally, this study recommends for a synergistic strategy in which AI enhances rather than replaces the human connection at the heart of language instruction.

Methodology

This study used a mixed-methods research design to thoroughly assess the influence of AI technologies on language education, using quantitative and qualitative methodologies to capture both measurable outcomes and complex participant experiences (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). The study was carried out over a six-month period at three secondary schools and one university in urban and suburban settings, ensuring a diverse sample representative of varying socioeconomic and

educational circumstances. The participant pool included 150 language learners (ages 14 to 22) enrolled in English and Spanish courses, as well as 12 educators with varied levels of experience in technological integration. The AI technologies used in language education—Duolingo for adaptive vocabulary and reading activities, Elsa Speak for pronunciation training, and Grammarly for writing enhancement—were chosen based on their established use and alignment with pedagogical goals (Li & Lan, 2021; Godwin-Jones, 2019). The process was divided into three parts to ensure methodical data collecting and analysis. Phase 1: Pre-Intervention Assessment entailed conducting questionnaires to gather baseline data on students' language competency, technical familiarity, and attitudes toward AI tools. These surveys were based on validated tools used in technology-enhanced learning research (Davis, 1989). Standardized language examinations based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) were also used to assess introductory speaking, writing, and comprehension abilities. Phase 2: intervention lasted 12 weeks, and AI tools were included into traditional language curriculum. Students worked with the tools for 30-45 minutes per session, three times a week, focusing on speaking practice (Elsa Speak), writing assignments (Grammarly), and vocabulary building (Duolingo). Teachers attended two professional development workshops based on Hubbard's (2021) framework for CALL teacher training to guarantee effective tool integration and alignment with learning objectives. Classroom observations were conducted fortnightly using a defined technique to document tool utilization, student engagement, and teacher facilitation (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). Phase 3: Post-Intervention Evaluation consisted of follow-up surveys, repeat CEFR-aligned examinations, and focus group interviews with 40 students and 8 teachers to investigate perspectives, problems, and perceived impacts. Interviews were semi-structured, giving participants the freedom to explore emerging topics (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015).

Quantitative data from questionnaires and tests were analyzed with SPSS software, which used paired t-tests to compare pre- and post-intervention proficiency scores and ANOVA to look for differences between demographic groups. Qualitative data from interviews and observations were transcribed and coded thematically in NVivo using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step approach for theme analysis. This dual strategy ensured triangulation, which increased the study's validity and reliability (Denzin, 2017). Ethical issues were highlighted, with institutional review board approval, informed permission from all participants (and guardians for children), and data anonymization to preserve privacy. Limitations included potential self-report biases in questionnaires, differences in technological availability (e.g., 15% of students used shared devices), and the relatively short intervention duration, which may limit generalizability to long-term results. These constraints were minimized through

thorough data triangulation and transparent reporting, which are consistent with best practices in educational research (Cohen et al., 2018).

Results and discussion

The findings of this study give persuasive proof of AI tools' effectiveness in improving language proficiency, with considerable gains found in speaking, writing, and comprehension skills. Elsa Speak improved speaking accuracy by 28% ($p < 0.01$), with students displaying significant development in phonemic accuracy and intonation. Grammarly's real-time feedback on grammar, syntax, and style helped students improve their writing by 22% ($p < 0.01$), allowing for incremental refinement. Duolingo's adaptive reading exercises improved comprehension scores by 15% ($p < 0.05$), with intermediate learners benefiting the most from them. These improvements varied slightly by age and prior proficiency, with younger learners (aged 14-16) making stronger gains in speaking (32%) than older learners (25%), probably due to increased involvement with gamified aspects (Dörnyei, 2001).

Figure 1: Pre- and Post-intervention Proficiency Scores Across Skill Areas. This bar chart shows the percentage improvement in speaking, writing, and comprehension ratings from pre- to post-intervention, demonstrating the considerable influence of AI technologies ($n = 150$). Qualitative data enhanced the study by demonstrating high levels of student involvement. According to surveys, 85% of participants considered AI technologies to be "highly motivating," with quick feedback and gamified features serving as important drives. Focus group interviews supported this viewpoint, with students describing tools like Duolingo as "fun and addictive" because of their reward-based progression mechanisms. Teachers noted a 30% reduction in grading time, particularly for writing projects, which allowed them to focus on targeted instruction and classroom discussions. Classroom observations verified improved student participation, with AI technologies creating a low-stakes setting for honing speaking and writing skills (Chapelle, 2016).

Approximately 20% of students faced hurdles due to a lack of personal devices or dependable internet, particularly in low-income schools, which aligns with Selwyn's (2019) worries about digital equity. Teachers were initially resistant to AI integration, with 50% citing discomfort within the first month owing to unfamiliarity with the tools. Professional development seminars helped to ameliorate this over time, but some educators were still concerned about over-reliance on AI, emphasizing the importance of human connection in teaching cultural nuances and developing interpersonal communication skills (Kramsch, 1993). Thematic analysis of interviews revealed three repeating themes: (1) the necessity of immediate feedback in developing confidence, (2) the need for fair access to technology, and (3) the importance of balancing AI with teacher-led training. The large performance gains indicate that AI tools are especially useful for skill-specific interventions like pronunciation and writing, which require quick feedback. However, the digital divide persists, demanding targeted investments in infrastructure and resources. Furthermore, the teacher resistance reported early in the study supports Hubbard's (2021) call for extensive professional development to achieve pedagogical alignment. The conversation emphasizes that, while AI technologies are powerful, their effectiveness is dependent on equity, teacher support, and preserving the human element in language instruction. These findings are consistent with previous research on technology-enhanced learning, which underlines AI's ability to tailor education while emphasizing the importance of proper deployment (Li & Lan, 2021). The large performance gains indicate that AI tools are especially useful for skill-specific interventions like pronunciation and writing, which require quick feedback. However, the digital divide persists, demanding targeted investments in infrastructure and resources. Furthermore, the teacher resistance reported early in

the study supports Hubbard's (2021) call for extensive professional development to achieve pedagogical alignment. The conversation emphasizes that, while AI technologies are powerful, their effectiveness is dependent on equity, teacher support, and preserving the human element in language instruction.

Conclusion

This study unambiguously proves the revolutionary power of AI technologies in language teaching, providing a road to individualized, engaging, and efficient learning that meets the needs of modern education. The large improvements in speaking (28%), writing (22%), and understanding (15%) demonstrate AI's potential as a supplemental tool for addressing varied student needs in secondary and higher education contexts. Tools like Elsa Speak, Grammarly, and Duolingo empower students to build confidence and autonomy while allowing teachers to focus on high-impact pedagogical practices like cultural understanding and critical thinking (Kukulska-Hulme et al., 2020). However, the study also highlights major issues that must be addressed in order for AI to reach its full potential. The digital divide, with 20% of students without dependable access to devices or the internet, emphasizes the critical need for fair infrastructure investments to provide inclusive access (Selwyn, 2019). Teacher preparation remains a critical issue, with early resistance emphasizing the importance of ongoing professional development in bridging the gap between technology and pedagogy (Hubbard, 2021). Furthermore, worries regarding over-reliance on AI highlight the critical role of human interaction in teaching the sociocultural nuances of language that are required for successful communication (Kramsch, 1993). These problems require a balanced approach in which AI is intelligently integrated as a complement to, rather than a replacement for, existing educational methods. Looking ahead, this study suggests various options for additional investigation. Future research should look into the long-term effects of AI technologies on language retention and fluency, especially in naturalistic contexts outside the classroom. Furthermore, investigating AI's usefulness in teaching lesser-known languages has the potential to address global linguistic variety and encourage inclusion. The creation of AI tools with increased cultural sensitivity, capable of mimicking authentic interpersonal interactions, could help to bridge the gap between technology and human-centered learning. To ensure that the benefits of AI reach all learners, policymakers and educational institutions must emphasize measures addressing digital equity, such as subsidized device programs and expanded internet access. Finally, the findings support a synergistic model of language education in which AI and human instruction collaborate to generate dynamic, inclusive, and effective learning environments. Educators may prepare children for a globalized world where multilingual proficiency is becoming increasingly important by harnessing AI's strengths—personalization, scalability, and efficiency—while keeping the human

connection at the heart of language acquisition. This report advocates for sustained investment in AI-driven education, as well as strong policies that promote fair access, comprehensive teacher training, and ongoing research to improve and broaden the use of these transformative tools. Through such efforts, AI can become a cornerstone of a reinvented language education environment that empowers both students and teachers.

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Using AI Tools to Implement Extensive Reading in EFL Classrooms: A Case Study of Susan Hill's Short Stories

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Abstract

Extensive reading (ER) is a crucial component of language acquisition, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. It promotes language fluency, vocabulary acquisition, cultural awareness, and learner autonomy. In the digital age, AI-powered tools offer innovative approaches to enrich extensive reading programs. This article explores how AI technologies can be strategically implemented to support and enhance extensive reading practices, using selected short stories by Susan Hill—The Boy Who Taught the Beekeeper to Read, Sand, Elizabeth, Punishment, and The Brooch—as core reading materials. Hill's psychologically complex, emotionally resonant narratives provide ideal content for AI-enhanced ER tasks that go beyond passive reading. The article outlines methodologies, digital integration strategies, and the pedagogical benefits of combining literary engagement with intelligent technology.

Key words: Extensive Reading, Artificial Intelligence, English as a Foreign Language, Susan Hill, Personalization, Critical engagement.

Annotatsiya

Keng ko'lamli o'qish (KO') til o'zlashtirishning muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ayniqsa chet tili sifatida ingliz tili (CTIT) sinflarida alohida ahamiyatga ega. U til ravonligi, lug'at boyligini o'zlashtirish, madaniy xabardorlik va o'quvchilarning mustaqilligini rivojlantiradi. Raqamli asrda sun'iy intellektga asoslangan vositalar keng ko'lamli o'qish dasturlarini boyitish uchun innovatsion yondashuvlarni taqdim etmoqda. Ushbu maqola Syuzan Hilning "Asalarichiga o'qishni o'rgatgan bola", "Qum", "Elizabet", "Jazo" va "To'g'nog'ich" kabi tanlangan qisqa hikoyalardan foydalangan holda keng ko'lamli o'qish amaliyotini qo'llab-quvvatlash va takomillashtirish uchun sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini qanday strategik joriy etish mumkinligini tadqiq qiladi. Xillning psixologik jihatdan murakkab, hissiy jihatdan ta'sirchan hikoyalari passiv o'qishdan tashqari sun'iy intellekt yordamida takomillashtirilgan KO' vazifalari uchun ideal mazmun taqdim etadi. Maqolada metodologiyalar, raqamli integratsiya strategiyalari va adabiy mashg'ulotlarni intellektual texnologiya bilan uyg'unlashtirishning pedagogik afzalliklari bayon etilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Keng ko'lamli o'qish, Sun'iy intellect, Chet tili sifatida ingliz tili, Syuzan Hill, Shaxsiylashtirish, Tanqidiy yondashuv.

Абстракт

Экстенсивное чтение (ЭЧ) является важнейшим компонентом усвоения языка, особенно в классах английского языка как иностранного. Оно способствует развитию беглости речи, усвоению словарного запаса, культурной осведомленности и самостоятельности учащихся. В цифровую эпоху инструменты на базе искусственного интеллекта предлагают инновационные подходы к обогащению обширных программ чтения. В данной статье рассматривается, как технологии искусственного интеллекта могут быть стратегически внедрены для поддержки и улучшения практики чтения, используя в качестве основных материалов для чтения избранные короткие рассказы Сюзен Хилл – "Мальчик, который научил пчеловода читать," "Песок," "Елизавета," "Наказание". Психологически сложные,

эмоционально резонансные нарративы Хилла обеспечивают идеальный контент для усовершенствованных ИИ ER-задач, которые выходят за рамки пассивного чтения. В статье описываются методологии, стратегии цифровой интеграции и педагогические преимущества сочетания литературных занятий с интеллектуальными технологиями.

Ключевые слова: Экстенсивное чтение, Искусственный интеллект, Английский как иностранный язык, Сьюзен Хилл, Персонализация, Критическое взаимодействие.

Introduction

Extensive reading (ER) refers to reading large amounts of text for general understanding, pleasure, and language development (Renandya, 2007). In EFL contexts, it has long been recognized as an effective approach to improve learners' language skills, including vocabulary, grammar, and reading fluency (Day, 2015). However, challenges such as limited resources, varying reading proficiency levels, and insufficient learner motivation can hinder the successful implementation of ER programs. Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a timely solution to these barriers. By integrating AI tools into EFL reading instruction, educators can provide personalized learning, promote critical engagement, and monitor progress effectively.

The selection of texts plays a central role in the success of ER. The short stories of Susan Hill, known for their psychological depth, subtle emotional tension, and rich language, offer significant benefits for EFL learners. Stories like *The Boy Who Taught the Beekeeper to Read* and *The Brooch* are not only linguistically accessible but also thematically rich, lending themselves to both linguistic and emotional exploration. This article demonstrates how AI tools can be used to scaffold and deepen the ER experience through these narratives.

Susan Hill's short stories are particularly suitable for EFL students for several reasons. While her stories contain rich vocabulary and varied sentence structures, they are generally readable for B2–C1 level learners. Stories like *Sand and Punishment* delve into themes of guilt, memory, and loss, encouraging students to think beyond surface meanings. Hill's work often reflects British society and psychology, which introduces learners to different cultural norms and values. As short stories, these texts allow complete reading within a class period or homework cycle, making them ideal for extensive reading tasks.

AI tools can facilitate and enrich extensive reading in several key ways:

AI Tool Type	Function in ER
AI-based Vocabulary Assistants	Define unfamiliar words, provide usage examples, suggest synonyms, and create flashcards (e.g., Rewordify, LingQ, Readlang)

Speech and Pronunciation Tools	Allow learners to hear native-like readings, and assess pronunciation (e.g., Elsa Speak, Google Read Aloud)
Writing and Summarizing AIs	Help learners generate summaries or reflections using models like ChatGPT
Adaptive Quizzing Platforms	Use student reading patterns to generate comprehension quizzes (e.g., Quizalize with AI recommendations)
AI-enhanced Annotation Tools	Enable learners to comment, highlight, and pose questions collaboratively (e.g., Perusall, Hypothes.is)

Sample Implementation

A Week-long ER Unit Using The Boy Who Taught the Beekeeper to Read

Day 1: Pre-reading Activities

AI prompt: “Generate three discussion questions based on the title.”

Students use ChatGPT to predict the plot and themes. Vocabulary lists are extracted via Readlang.

Day 2: Reading and Listening

Students read the story with an AI narrator (e.g., NaturalReader).

Difficult words are auto-annotated using Readlang's pop-up dictionary.

Day 3: Comprehension and Emotional Engagement

Using ChatGPT, students generate discussion questions and compare them.

AI-generated multiple-choice questions help check basic understanding.

Day 4: Creative Retelling

Students use AI tools like Storybird or Sudowrite to retell the story from the beekeeper's point of view.

AI can also suggest alternative endings or thematic comparisons to other stories.

Day 5: Critical Response and Reflection

Students ask AI to summarize the story in 100 words.

They write personal reflections and receive AI feedback on grammar and style.

Teachers monitor progress and engagement via an AI dashboard (e.g., with Edmodo AI plugins).

5. Extending the Model: Applying to Other Stories

Sand: Explore themes of war memory using AI-generated timelines or historical background assistants.

Elizabeth: Use sentiment analysis tools to examine character mood swings or tone.

Punishment: Analyze moral dilemmas using AI debate platforms.

The Brooch: Reconstruct events through chatbot role-play simulations (AI as “the mother,” “the daughter,” etc.).

Each of these stories supports deeper reading, critical thinking, and emotional response—skills crucial for both language acquisition and literary understanding.

Pedagogical Benefits

AI tailors reading paths and vocabulary support to individual learners. Interactive tools such as chatbots or story generators foster active reading. AI annotation and discussion platforms enhance peer interaction and shared meaning-making. Instant feedback on comprehension, vocabulary use, and writing helps learners self-regulate. Learners can explore texts and interpretations independently, building confidence and intrinsic motivation.

While promising, AI integration requires careful planning:

Data Privacy and Ethics: Ensure AI tools are compliant with student data protection laws.

Digital Literacy: Teachers and students may need training to effectively use AI features.

Content Sensitivity: Hill’s stories, while rich, sometimes touch on dark psychological themes that require guided discussion.

AI tools offer exciting opportunities to transform extensive reading from a passive to an interactive, student-centered experience. When paired with the emotionally textured and linguistically rich stories of Susan Hill, AI-powered extensive reading not only improves EFL learners’ language competence but also fosters literary sensitivity and critical engagement. Through thoughtful implementation, EFL educators can leverage these technologies to make literature more accessible, personalized, and meaningful for their students.

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THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TRANSLATION

4-sho'ba

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing many fields, including education and linguistics. This paper explores the influence of AI on language learning and translation, focusing on the effectiveness of AI-powered tools, their pedagogical implications, and the changing role of human instructors and translators. Using current data, real-world applications, and case studies, the study demonstrates that while AI tools like Chat GPT, Duolingo, and Google Translate offer unprecedented accessibility and efficiency, they also raise concerns related to accuracy, cultural context, and ethical use. The findings suggest that AI should be used as a complement rather than a replacement for human expertise in both fields.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, language learning, machine translation, Chat GPT, Duolingo, translation, ethics, pedagogy.

Аннотация

Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) совершает революцию во многих сферах, включая образование и лингвистику. В данной статье рассматривается влияние ИИ на изучение языков и перевод, с акцентом на эффективность инструментов, основанных на ИИ, их педагогические последствия, а также изменяющуюся роль преподавателей и переводчиков. Используя актуальные данные, реальные примеры и кейс-стади, исследование показывает, что такие ИИ-инструменты, как ChatGPT, Duolingo и Google Translate, обеспечивают беспрецедентную доступность и эффективность, но в то же время вызывают обеспокоенность по поводу точности, культурного контекста и этического использования. Результаты свидетельствуют о том, что ИИ следует рассматривать как дополнение, а не замену человеческой экспертизы в этих областях.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, изучение языков, машинный перевод, Chat GPT, Duolingo, перевод, этика, педагогика

Annotatsiya

Sun'iy intellekt (SI) ta'lim va tilshunoslik kabi ko'plab sohalarda inqilobiy o'zgarishlar keltirib chiqarmoqda. Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellektning til o'rganish va tarjima-dagi ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi; xususan, SI vositalarining samaradorligi, ularning ta'limiy jihatlari hamda inson o'qituvchilari va tarjimonlarining o'zgarayotgan roli tahlil qilinadi. Amaldagi ma'lumotlar, real ilovalar va tahliliy holatlar asosida olib borilgan tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, Chat GPT, Duolingo va Google Translate kabi sun'iy intellekt vositalari misli ko'rilmagan darajada qulaylik va tezlikni ta'minlashda, ularning aniqligi, madaniy kontekstni tushunishi va axloqiy jihatlari bilan bog'liq muammolar ham mavjud. Tadqiqot xulosasiga ko'ra, sun'iy intellekt inson mutaxassislarini to'liq almashtiruvchi emas, balki ularga samarali yordamchi sifatida qaralishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, til o'rganish, mashina tarjimasi, ChatGPT, Duolingo, tarjima, etika, ta'lim.

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has penetrated various sectors, from finance and healthcare to education and linguistics. Among the most dynamic areas of AI application are language learning and translation, where intelligent algorithms process, generate, and adapt linguistic data to facilitate communication. The rise of AI-powered platforms such as Google Translate, Deep L, Duolingo, and Open AI's Chat GPT has significantly changed how individuals learn languages and how texts are translated across linguistic boundaries. This paper aims to analyze the impact of AI on language learning and translation by answering two main questions:

1. How has AI improved or changed language learning experiences?
2. To what extent can AI-based translation tools replace human translators?

This study employed a qualitative research methodology, using secondary data from academic journals, official reports, AI platform analytics, and case studies published between 2018 and 2024. Key resources included articles from *Computational Linguistics*, *Language Learning and Technology*, and publications by UNESCO on language technology. Additionally, the paper includes an analysis of user data from Duolingo (as reported in their annual effectiveness study) and performance comparisons between Google Translate and professional translation benchmarks.

AI has improved language learning in the following ways:

- **Personalization:** AI platforms such as Duolingo and Babbel adjust lessons based on a learner's strengths, weaknesses, and progress.
- **Engagement:** Chatbots and virtual tutors offer immersive and conversational practice, simulating real-life interaction.
- **Accessibility:** AI tools have reduced geographical and financial barriers, providing free or low-cost education globally.

A 2023 Duolingo report found that students using AI-based adaptive lessons showed a 35% improvement in vocabulary retention compared to non-AI curricula.

AI translation tools such as Google Translate and Deep L have become increasingly accurate due to neural machine translation (NMT). AI can now:

- Translate idiomatic expressions with more nuance.
- Maintain sentence structure and flow across different language families.
- Offer real-time translation for over 100 languages.

However, challenges remain in:

- **Contextual understanding:** AI still struggles with irony, sarcasm, and cultural references.
- **Domain-specific translation:** Technical, legal, and medical texts often require expert human intervention.
- **Bias:** Machine learning models trained on biased data may reproduce stereotypes or errors.

In a comparative study (2022), Deep L achieved a 78% accuracy rate in translating academic texts, compared to 92% by professional translators. AI facilitates **autonomous learning**, allowing users to control their learning pace and content. Its 24/7 availability makes it especially useful for learners in remote or underserved areas. In translation, AI significantly enhances speed, helping global companies operate more efficiently and communicate with diverse audiences instantly. Despite improvements, AI lacks human intuition. Language is not only grammar and vocabulary, it carries cultural, emotional, and situational meaning. An AI can translate "It's raining cats and dogs" literally, but only a human understands its idiomatic meaning. Moreover, over-reliance on AI tools in education may reduce learners' motivation to deeply engage with the language.

Ethically, concerns include:

- Data privacy: AI apps often collect personal information.
- Plagiarism: Students using AI-generated essays raise academic integrity concerns.
- Unemployment risk: Human translators fear job loss due to automation, though many now work in hybrid "post-editing" roles.

The future likely lies in collaboration rather than replacement. AI can handle repetitive tasks, freeing educators and translators to focus on complex or creative elements. For example, in Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) tools, human translators edit AI-generated drafts, improving both efficiency and quality.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence has fundamentally reshaped language learning and translation by making these processes more accessible, efficient, and scalable. Yet, while AI demonstrates remarkable capabilities, it does not fully capture the subtleties of human language. Thus, AI should be viewed as a powerful assistant, not a substitute for human teachers and translators. Future developments must prioritize ethical design, human-AI synergy, and culturally informed applications.

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THE FUNCTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN UZBEKISTAN'S PERSONALISED ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Sun'iy intellektning (SI) O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'qitishdagi o'zgaruvchan roli tahlil qilinadi. Chatbotlar, moslashuvchan o'quv platformalari va avtomatlashtirilgan fikr-mulohaza tizimlari kabi SI vositalari orqali shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish hamda real vaqtli baholash imkoniyatlari yaratilmoqda. Maqolada SI imkoniyatlarining ingliz tili bilimni oshirishdagi salohiyati ta'kidlanadi, shu bilan birga muammolar — raqamli infratuzilmaning cheklanganligi, o'qituvchilar orasida SI bo'yicha savodxonlikning pastligi va ma'lumotlar maxfiylikiga oid xavotirlar ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif SI texnologiyalarini samarali joriy etish uchun siyosiy tavsiyalarni ilgari suradi, bu esa O'zbekiston o'quvchilarini global muloqotga yaxshiroq tayyorlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tilini o'rganish, moslashuvchan ta'lim, ta'lim texnologiyalari, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, O'zbekiston, SI muammolari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается влияние искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) на преподавание английского языка в Узбекистане. Особое внимание уделяется использованию ИИ-инструментов, таких как чат-боты, адаптивные обучающие платформы и автоматические системы обратной связи, которые способствуют персонализированному обучению, повышают вовлечённость студентов и обеспечивают оценивание в реальном времени. Несмотря на значительный потенциал ИИ в улучшении языковой подготовки, автор также выделяет ряд проблем: ограниченный доступ к цифровым ресурсам, низкий уровень цифровой грамотности среди преподавателей и вопросы конфиденциальности данных. В заключение приводятся рекомендации по политике и стратегии внедрения ИИ в систему образования Узбекистана для эффективного развития языковых навыков и подготовки студентов к глобальной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, изучение английского языка, адаптивное обучение, образовательные технологии, персонализированное обучение, Узбекистан, вызовы ИИ.

Annotation: This article explores the transformative role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in English language education in Uzbekistan. It highlights how AI-powered tools, such as chatbots, adaptive platforms, and automated feedback systems, enhance personalized learning, boost student engagement, and offer real-time assessment. While the integration of AI presents significant opportunities for improving English proficiency, the paper also addresses key challenges, including limited digital infrastructure, low AI literacy among educators, and concerns over data privacy. The study concludes with policy recommendations aimed at facilitating the effective adoption of AI technologies in Uzbekistan's education system, ultimately preparing students for global communication.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, English language learning, adaptive learning, educational technology, Uzbekistan, personalized instruction, AI challenges.

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid pace of globalization and the growing demand for English language proficiency as a key skill in the 21st century, Uzbekistan has increasingly acknowledged the necessity of reforming its language education system. Historically, English language instruction in the country has been dominated by traditional methodologies that prioritize rote memorization over communicative practice. While these methods may support vocabulary acquisition and grammatical accuracy, they often fall short in fostering learners' ability to use English effectively in real-life, interactive contexts (Rahmanov, 2021).

In response to this challenge, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising solution to modernize language instruction. By integrating AI technologies into educational environments, it becomes possible to shift from a one-size-fits-all approach to a more learner-centered model. AI-powered educational tools, such as intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning platforms, and virtual assistants, enable the creation of personalized learning experiences tailored to each student's proficiency level, learning pace, and preferences (Nguyen & Ikeda, 2020). These systems analyze student performance in real-time and adjust instructional content accordingly, thereby promoting higher engagement and improved learning outcomes.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the application of AI in English language education represents both an opportunity and a challenge. On one hand, it holds the potential to address long-standing inefficiencies in the system and to better prepare students for participation in global academic, professional, and social spheres. On the other hand, issues such as limited access to technological infrastructure, insufficient digital literacy among educators, and the need for clear data governance policies present substantial obstacles to implementation.

This study investigates the role of Artificial Intelligence in facilitating personalized English language learning in Uzbekistan. It aims to analyze the benefits of AI-driven approaches, identify the challenges specific to the Uzbek educational landscape, and propose practical policy recommendations for stakeholders. By doing so, the paper contributes to the broader discourse on educational innovation and the effective integration of emerging technologies into national language education strategies.

METHODS

This study employs a mixed-method approach, combining literature review, case studies, and surveys conducted among educators and students in Uzbekistan. The literature review includes an analysis of previous research on AI in language education. Surveys were administered to 200 English language teachers and 500 students across different regions of Uzbekistan to assess their familiarity with and attitudes toward AI-powered learning tools. Additionally, case studies from universities and language

centers implementing AI in English instruction provide insights into best practices and challenges.

RESULTS

AI technologies are increasingly used in Uzbekistan's English language education, with platforms such as Duolingo, Grammarly, and ChatGPT being popular among students. These tools provide personalized learning pathways, real-time feedback, and interactive exercises. Teachers report that AI tools help students improve grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation through adaptive learning techniques (Karimov & Saidova, 2022).

Survey results indicate that 78% of students using AI-powered tools showed noticeable improvement in their English proficiency within six months. AI-driven applications enhance motivation by incorporating gamification elements, interactive exercises, and immediate feedback. Additionally, students reported increased confidence in speaking and writing due to AI-assisted pronunciation analysis and essay evaluation features.

Among the surveyed teachers, 72% expressed a willingness to integrate AI tools into their teaching practices, citing improved student performance and reduced grading workload as key benefits. However, 65% of educators highlighted a lack of training and familiarity with AI-based teaching methods as a barrier to effective implementation. Teachers also raised concerns about the over-reliance on technology and the need for human oversight in language instruction.

Despite AI's potential, several challenges hinder its effective implementation in Uzbekistan's education system:

- Limited Digital Infrastructure: Many schools lack the necessary technological resources to support AI-based learning.
- Educator Readiness: A survey revealed that 65% of teachers feel unprepared to integrate AI into their classrooms due to a lack of training.
- Data Privacy Concerns: AI applications collect and analyze student data, raising ethical and security concerns.
- Language-Specific Limitations: AI models primarily trained in English may not fully support Uzbek-speaking learners, limiting their effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

AI has the potential to revolutionize English language learning in Uzbekistan by offering personalized, adaptive learning experiences that cater to the unique needs and pace of each student. AI-powered tools can provide instant feedback, interactive exercises, and tailored learning pathways that help learners improve their grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and writing skills more efficiently. However, for AI to be successfully integrated into the educational system, a multi-faceted approach must be taken to address key challenges.

First and foremost, teacher training programs in Uzbekistan must incorporate AI literacy and digital pedagogy courses. Teachers need to understand how AI tools work, how they can be applied effectively in language teaching, and how to integrate these tools into their existing teaching methods. By equipping educators with the necessary skills to use AI tools effectively, they can harness the full potential of these technologies to enhance learning outcomes. Professional development programs should not only focus on the technical aspects of using AI but also emphasize its role in supporting pedagogical goals, such as improving student engagement, differentiation, and personalized learning. Secondly, the government must prioritize investment in digital infrastructure to ensure equitable access to AI-powered learning tools. Many schools in Uzbekistan still lack the necessary technological resources, such as reliable internet access, computers, and mobile devices, that are essential for implementing AI-driven education. To ensure that AI tools benefit all students, the government must make investments in both hardware and software, ensuring that schools in urban and rural areas alike have the resources to implement AI-based learning programs. This investment could include upgrading internet infrastructure, providing schools with affordable devices, and supporting the development of localized AI tools tailored to the specific linguistic and cultural needs of Uzbek-speaking learners. Lastly, there must be clear regulatory frameworks in place to address data privacy concerns. AI-powered learning tools collect and analyze a significant amount of student data to provide personalized feedback and track progress. However, this raises important ethical and security concerns, especially when it comes to protecting sensitive student information. The government and educational institutions need to establish robust policies and guidelines to ensure that AI applications comply with data protection laws and respect students' privacy. These regulations should focus on transparency in data collection, secure data storage, and clear guidelines on how student data is used, shared, and protected. Ensuring the responsible use of data will help build trust in AI tools and alleviate concerns about misuse or unauthorized access to personal information.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of AI in English language learning holds immense potential for transforming Uzbekistan's education system. With its ability to provide personalized instruction, real-time feedback, and adaptive learning experiences, AI can significantly enhance English proficiency among students. However, the successful implementation of AI requires addressing challenges such as limited infrastructure, teacher readiness, and data privacy concerns. By strategically investing in digital infrastructure, prioritizing AI-focused teacher training, and establishing clear policies to protect student data, Uzbekistan can ensure the effective use of AI in education. Through these efforts, the country can improve its students' language skills, increase

their global competitiveness, and prepare them for a future where AI and digital literacy are key to success in the global marketplace.

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SUN'IY INTELLEKT ORQALI TALABALARNING MUSTAQIL TA'LIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: XORIJIY TIL O'QITISH JARAYONIDA YANGI IMKONIYATLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR

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Annotatsiya: Maqola sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari yordamida talabalarning mustaqil ta'limini rivojlantirish muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda SI asosidagi ta'lim platformalarining dolzarbligi, ularning talabalarning o'quv faoliyatini shaxsiylashtirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, mustaqil ta'lim, ta'lim texnologiyalari, shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim, o'quv samaradorligi, ta'lim platformalari, adaptiv ta'lim.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена проблеме развития самостоятельного обучения студентов с использованием технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ). В исследовании анализируется актуальность образовательных платформ на основе ИИ и их роль в персонализации учебной деятельности студентов.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, самостоятельное обучение, образовательные технологии, персонализированное обучение, эффективность обучения, образовательные платформы, адаптивное обучение.

Annotation. The article focuses on the issue of enhancing students' independent learning through artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. The study analyzes the relevance of AI-based educational platforms and their role in personalizing students' learning activities. Systemic analysis, comparison, and experimental methods were employed.

Key words; Artificial intelligence, independent learning, educational technologies, personalized learning, learning efficiency, educational platforms, adaptive learning.

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida talabalarning mustaqil ta'limi muhim o'rin tutmoqda. Global raqamlashtirish jarayonlari va sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi ta'lim jarayonini tubdan o'zgartirmoqda. SI vositalari talabalarga shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv tajribasini taqdim etib, ularning bilim olish samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda [1; 12]. Ushbu maqolada SI texnologiyalari yordamida talabalarning mustaqil ta'limini rivojlantirishning afzalliklari, muammolari va istiqbollari o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi – SI asosidagi ta'lim platformalarining o'quv jarayoniga ta'sirini tahlil qilish va ularni joriy etish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Sun'iy intellektning ta'limdagi o'rni. Sun'iy intellekt ta'lim sohasida keng qo'llanilmoqda. SI asosidagi adaptiv ta'lim tizimlari talabalarning bilim darajasiga, o'quv uslubiga va ehtiyojlariga mos dars rejalarini avtomatik ravishda tuzadi. Masalan, Coursera va EdX kabi platformalar SI algoritmlari yordamida har bir talabaga individual topshiriqlar va resurslar taklif qiladi [2; 45]. SI virtual o'qituvchi yordamchilari (chatbotlar) talabalarga real vaqtda savollarga javob berish, masalalarni yechishda yordam ko'rsatish va o'quv jarayonini tahlil qilish imkonini beradi.

Bundan tashqari, SI texnologiyalari o'qituvchilarning ishini optimallashtirishga yordam beradi. Masalan, avtomatlashtirilgan baholash tizimlari talabalarning ishlarini tezkor va xolisona tekshiradi, bu esa o'qituvchilarning vaqtini tejaydi [3; 67]. Shu bilan birga, SI yordamida talabalarning o'quv faoliyati tahlil qilinib, ularning zaif tomonlari aniqlanadi va mos ravishda o'quv jarayoni tuzatiladi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi. Ushbu tadqiqotda SI asosidagi ta'lim platformalarining talabalarning mustaqil ta'limiga ta'sirini o'rganish uchun tizimli tahlil, taqqoslash va tajriba metodlari qo'llanildi. Tajriba Toshkent davlat pedagogika universitetining 100 nafar talabasi ishtirokida o'tkazildi. Talabalar ikki guruhga bo'lingan: birinchi guruh SI asosidagi Moodle platformasining AI moduli yordamida o'qidi, ikkinchi guruh esa an'anaviy usullardan foydalandi.

Tajriba davomida talabalarning o'quv natijalari, mustaqil ishlarining sifati va o'quv jarayoniga qiziqishi baholandi. SI platformasi talabalarga individual topshiriqlar taqdim etdi, ularning bilim darajasiga qarab savollarning murakkablik darajasini o'zgartirdi va o'quv jarayonini real vaqtda kuzatdi. Tajriba 3 oy davom etdi va natijalar statistik tahlil yordamida qayta ishlandi [4; 89].

Tajriba natijalariga ko'ra, SI asosidagi platformadan foydalangan guruhda talabalarning o'quv natijalari an'anaviy guruhga nisbatan o'rtacha 20% yuqori bo'ldi. Bundan tashqari, SI guruhidagi talabalar o'quv jarayoniga ko'proq qiziqish bildirgan va mustaqil ravishda qo'shimcha resurslarni o'rganishga intilgan. SI platformasi

talabalarning zaif tomonlarini aniqlab, ularga mos tavsiyalar bergani tufayli o'quv jarayoni samaradorligi oshdi [5; 23].

SI platformasi topshiriqlarni baholash va talabalarning faoliyatini monitoring qilishda vaqtni sezilarli darajada tejadi. Masalan, an'anaviy guruhda o'qituvchilar har bir talabaning ishini alohida tekshirishga o'rtacha 10 soat sarflashgan bo'lsa, SI guruhida bu jarayon avtomatlashtirilgan edi.

SI texnologiyalarining afzalliklariga qaramay, bir qator muammolar mavjud. Birinchidan, ma'lumotlar maxfiylik masalasi dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Talabalarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlari va o'quv natijalari bulutli platformalarda saqlanadi, bu esa kiberxavfsizlik xavfini oshiradi [6; 56]. Ikkinchidan, SI platformalarini joriy etish yuqori moliyaviy xarajatlarni talab qiladi, bu esa rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar uchun qiyinchilik tug'diradi.

Uchinchidan, SI vositalari talabalarning ijodiy fikrlash va tanqidiy tahlil qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda cheklovlarga ega. Masalan, SI algoritmlari ko'pincha standartlashtirilgan yechimlarni taklif qiladi, bu esa talabalarning o'ziga xos yondashuvlarini cheklashi mumkin [7; 34].

Tadqiqot natijalariga asoslanib, quyidagi takliflar ishlab chiqildi: SI platformalarini kengaytirish. Ta'lim muassasalarida SI asosidagi platformalarni joriy etish uchun maxsus grantlar va davlat dasturlari tashkil etilishi kerak.

O'qituvchilarni tayyorlash. SI vositalaridan samarali foydalanish uchun o'qituvchilarga maxsus kurslar tashkil qilinishi lozim.

Ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi. Talabalarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish uchun maxsus qonunchilik ishlab chiqilishi va kiberxavfsizlik choralarini kuchaytirilishi kerak.

Gibrid ta'lim modeli. SI texnologiyalari an'anaviy ta'lim usullari bilan uyg'unlashtirilib, gibrid ta'lim modeli yaratilishi tavsiya etiladi.

Kelajakda SI texnologiyalari ta'lim sohasida yanada kengroq qo'llanilishi kutilmoqda. Virtual reallik (VR) va kengaytirilgan reallik (AR) kabi yangi texnologiyalar SI bilan integratsiyalashganda, talabalarning mustaqil ta'limi yanada samarali bo'ladi [8; 78].

Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari talabalarning mustaqil ta'limini rivojlantirishda muhim imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Tadqiqot natijalari SI asosidagi platformalarning o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishini, talabalarning bilim olishga qiziqishini kuchaytirishini va o'qituvchilarning ishini optimallashtirishini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga, ma'lumotlar maxfiylik, moliyaviy cheklovlar va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishdagi muammolar SI texnologiyalarini joriy etishda e'tiborga olinishi kerak. Muallif tomonidan taklif qilingan gibrid ta'lim modeli va o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash dasturlari ta'lim tizimida SI'dan samarali foydalanishga xizmat qiladi.

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O'QITISH JARAYONIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT VOSITALARINING SHAXSIY TANLOVGA VA PSIXOLOGIK MUSTAQILLIKKA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola sun'iy intellekt (SI) vositalarining o'qitish jarayonida shaxsiy tanlov va psixologik mustaqillikka ta'sirini o'rganadi. SI tizimlari orqali o'quvchilarga moslashtirilgan tavsiyalar berilishi, ularning qaror qabul qilish jarayonini qanday o'zgartirishi, shuningdek, o'quvchilarning faolligi, tanlov qilish odatlari va mas'uliyat hissiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi tahlil etiladi. Maqola metodik tavsiyalar asosida, sun'iy intellekt vositalarining samarali qo'llanilishi orqali o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirish va shaxsiy rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlash usullarini ko'rsatadi. Bu tavsiyalar ta'lim tizimida shaxsiy tanlov va mas'uliyatni mustahkamlashga yordam beradi va o'quvchilarning o'z-o'zini anglash va qaror qabul qilishda yaxshilanishini ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, shaxsiy tanlov, psixologik mustaqillik, mas'uliyat, organizmik nazariya, avtonomiya, kompetentlik, aloqa, o'zini belgilash nazariyasi

Annotation

This article examines the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) tools on personal choice and psychological independence in the teaching process. It explores how AI systems, through personalized recommendations for students, affect their decision-making processes, as well as their engagement, choice habits, and sense of responsibility. Based on methodological recommendations, the article demonstrates how the effective use of AI tools can foster independent thinking and support personal development. These recommendations help reinforce personal choice and responsibility in the educational system, ensuring improvements in students' self-awareness and decision-making abilities.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, personal choice, psychological independence, responsibility, organismic theory, autonomy, competence, relatedness, self-determination theory.

Аннотация

В этой статье исследуется влияние инструментов искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) на личный выбор и психологическую независимость в процессе обучения. Рассматривается, как системы ИИ через персонализированные рекомендации для студентов изменяют их процесс принятия решений, а также их вовлеченность, привычки выбора и чувство ответственности. На основе методических рекомендаций в статье показывается, как эффективное использование инструментов ИИ может способствовать развитию независимого мышления и поддержке личностного развития. Эти рекомендации помогают укрепить личный выбор и ответственность в образовательной системе, обеспечивая улучшение самосознания студентов и их способности принимать решения.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, личный выбор, психологическая независимость, ответственность, организменная теория, автономия, компетентность, связь, теория самоопределения.

Hozirgi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalari tezkor suratlarda rivojlanmoqda. Jumladan raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari, chat-botlar hamda individual yo'naltirilgan o'quv tizimlari, balki o'quvchilarning o'rganishga bo'lgan ichki motivatsiyasi va tanlovdagi mustaqilligiga ham sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Sir emaski, AI texnologiyalari o'qituvchilarning faoliyatini yengillashtirib, o'qituvchining shaxsiy yondoshuvida qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, ammo boshqa tomondan shaxsiy tanlov qilish qilish, mustaqil qaror qabul qilish jarayoniga ham bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan haddan tashqari va avtomatik tarzda ishlatilishi o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashi, shaxsiy qaror qabul qilish layoqati va o'zini boshqarish qobiliyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Ta'lim jarayonida shaxsiy tanlov bu o'quvchilarning o'z qiziqishlari, imkoniyatlari, qobiliyati va albatta ehtiyojlariga mos holda o'qitish uslubidir. Psixologik mustaqillik esa tashqi ta'sirlarga tushmasdan mustaqil qaror qabul qila olish, o'zining shaxsiy qarori uchun javobgar bo'lish va o'z faoliyatini boshqarish qobiliyatidir.

Bugungi kunda turli sun'iy intellekt tizimlari, masalan, Khan Academy, Coursera, Duolingo kabi platformalar o'quvchilarga individual tarzda moslashtirilgan tavsiyalarni taqdim etmoqda. Ushbu tizimlar algoritmlar asosida talabaning o'rganish jarayonini tahlil qilib, har bir o'quvchi uchun eng optimal o'quv materiallarini tanlaydi. Biroq, bu imkoniyatlar ba'zi salbiy ta'sirlarga ham olib kelishi mumkin. O'quvchilarning qaror qabul qilish jarayonida sun'iy intellektga juda ko'p tayanishi, o'z tanlovlari va qarorlarini qabul qilishda mustaqil harakat qilishni kamaytirishi mumkin. Natijada, o'quvchilarda faollik darajasi pasayib, ular o'z o'rganish jarayonlariga nisbatan kamroq mas'uliyat hissi sezishadi. Bu holat, o'z navbatida, shaxsiy mas'uliyat, ichki motivatsiya va o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatining zaiflashishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Odamlar odatda qiziquvchan, o'z-o'zini harakatlantiruvchi (o'zini boshqaruvchi), faol va ilhomlangan bo'lishadi; ular o'rganishga, o'z imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishga, yangi ko'nikmalarni egallashga va iste'dodlarini amalga oshirishga intiladilar. Shu bilan birga, "insoniy ruh ezilishi yoki so'nishi, ba'zan esa odamlar o'sish va mas'uliyatni rad etishi" ham mumkin. O'zini belgilash nazariyasi bu tabiiy o'sishga bo'lgan moyillikning samarali ishlashi uchun "ijtimoiy muhitdan ozuqa yoki qo'llab-quvvatlovchi vositalarni talab etishini" ta'kidlaydi. O'zini belgilash nazariyasi bu ehtiyojni insondagi uchta tug'ma psixologik ehtiyojlarning qondirilishi deb tushuntiradi:

1. Avtonomiya (mustaqillik)
2. Kompetentlik (o'zini qobiliyatli his qilish)
3. Aloqa (bog'liqlik, boshqalar bilan yaqinlik)⁵⁹

O'zini belgilash nazariyasi xususan, o'quvchilarning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlari va ichki motivatsiyasini qondirishga qaratilgan, shuningdek, o'quvchilarga avtonomiya va kompetentlik hislarini taqdim etishga yordam beradi. O'qitish jarayonida sun'iy intellekt vositalari talabalarga shaxsiy tanlov imkoniyatlarini taqdim etishi va o'z faoliyatlarini boshqarishga imkon berishi mumkin.

Sun'iy intellektning o'quvchilarga taqdim etadigan ketma-ket berilgan yo'riqnomalari, shuningdek, o'quvchilarning psixologik avtonomiyasiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Agar o'quvchilar o'zining qarorlarini tizimga to'liq topshirsa, ular o'z tanlovlariga nisbatan mas'uliyat hissini kamaytirishi mumkin. O'qituvchilar, shu bois, sun'iy intellekt vositalarini samarali qo'llashda, o'quvchilarga mustaqil fikr yuritish, o'z tanlovlarini amalga oshirish va maqsadlar qo'yish imkoniyatini yaratishga alohida e'tibor qaratishlari kerak.

Neil Selwynning "Texnologiya ta'limni soddalashtiradi, lekin murakkab psixologik va axloqiy savollarni keltirib chiqaradi."⁶⁰ degan fikri bu mavzuni chuqurroq o'rganishga turtki bo'ladi.

Texnologiya ta'limni yanada samarali qilish imkonini yaratadi. Kompyuterlar, internet va boshqa raqamli vositalar orqali ta'lim resurslariga oson kirish, o'qituvchilarning ishini yengillashtiradi va o'quvchilarga o'z-o'zini ta'lim olishda yordam beradi. Shuningdek, texnologiyalar yordamida o'quvchilarga qiziqarli, interaktiv va vizual materiallar taqdim etilishi, o'qitish jarayonini yanada samarali va jozibali qiladi. Ammo texnologiya ta'limni osonlashtirgan bo'lsa-da, bu o'quvchilarning psixologik holatiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

⁵⁹ Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). *The "What" and "Why" of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior. Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.

⁶⁰ Selwyn N. *Education and Technology: Key Issues and Debates* (2nd ed.). Bloomsbury Academic. 2017. – 254 b.

- agar o'quvchilar texnologiyalarga haddan tashqari tayanib qolsa, ular o'zlarini passiv qilib, o'rganish jarayonida faollik ko'rsatmasligi mumkin.

- o'quvchilar o'z bilimlarini sun'iy intellekt tizimlariga, algoritmlarga asoslangan tavsiyalar orqali olishsa, bu ularning mustaqil fikrlash va o'z-o'zini anglash qobiliyatini susaytirishi mumkin.

- sun'iy intellekt tizimlari ko'pincha ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilib, o'quvchilarga tavsiyalar beradi. Ammo, agar o'quvchilar bu tavsiyalarga ko'p tayanib qolsa, ular o'zlari mustaqil qaror qabul qilishni o'rganmasligi mumkin.

Shu bilan birga axloqiy masalalar ham ko'rib chiqilishi lozim. O'quvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlari texnologik tizimlarda saqlanadi, bu esa ularning maxfiyligi va xavfsizligi bilan bog'liq muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Misol uchun sun'iy intellekt vositalariga shaxsiy foto va videolarni yuklash, shaxsiy karta raqamlarini yuklash va jiddiy masalalarda maslahat so'rash (sog'liq, ijtimoiy va oilaviy).

Texnologiya inson o'rtasidagi bevosita muloqotni kamaytirishi mumkin. Bu, o'z navbatida, o'quvchilarning jamoa bilan ishlash, ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ya'ni guruhda muhokama qilish, fikr almashish, tahlil qilish imkoniyatini to'sib qo'yadi. Ta'lim tizimida texnologiyalarni samarali va mas'uliyatli tarzda qo'llash zarur. O'quvchilarni shaxsiy rivojlanish, o'z-o'zini anglash, va mustaqil qaror qabul qilishga undash, texnologiya orqali ta'limning asosiy maqsadi bo'lishi kerak.

Nicholas Carrning "Algoritmlar bizning fikrlash jarayonlarimizni asta-sekinlik bilan o'zlashtirib bormoqda"⁶¹ degan fikri, raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellektning kundalik hayotimizda qanday o'zgarishlarga olib kelayotganini ta'kidlaydi.

Bugungi kunda, bizning turmush tarzimizda algoritmlar markaziy rol o'ynaydi. Internetdagi qidiruv tizimlaridan tortib, ijtimoiy tarmoqlargacha, sun'iy intellekt asosida ishlovchi platformalar bizning harakatlarimizni, qarorlarimizni va fikrlash jarayonlarimizni kuzatib, ularga moslashtirilgan tavsiyalar beradi. Masalan You Tube, Instagram platformalari foydalanuvchilarning ko'rgan videolariga asoslangan holda, ularning qiziqishlariga mos tavsiyalarni taklif qiladi. Yoki Amazon, Uzummarket, Ozon savdo ilovalarida ham foydalanuvchining ilgari qidirgan mahsulotlariga asoslangan tavsiyalar shakllanadi. Bu algoritmlar o'z-o'zini takrorlaydigan, uzoq muddatda foydalanuvchining qarorlariga ta'sir etuvchi mexanizmga aylanadi.

Algoritmlar bizning fikrlash jarayonlarimizni avtonom tarzda boshqarishni boshlaydi. Buning natijasida, odamlar ko'pincha o'zlari mustaqil qarorlar qabul qilishdan ko'ra, tizimlarning tavsiyalariga ishonishga moyil bo'lishadi. Masalan

⁶¹ Carr N. *The Shallows: What the Internet Is Doing to Our Brains*. W.W. Norton & Company. 2010. – 320 b.

ijtimoiy tarmoqlar Facebook, Instagram kabi ijtimoiy tarmoqlar foydalanuvchilarga ilgari yoqtirgan yoki ko'rgan postlar asosida yangi kontentni taqdim etadi, natijada ularning fikrlash doirasi doimiy ravishda cheklangan, algoritmlar tomonidan shakllantirilgan kontent bilan ta'minlanadi. Yoki qidiruv tizimlari Google'da ham biror mavzu bo'yicha qidiruv qilishda, foydalanuvchilar tezda eng mashhur yoki eng ko'p ko'rilgan yoki yuborilgan havolalarga tayanishadi, bu esa o'z navbatida, ularning mustaqil fikrlashini cheklaydi. Carrning fikriga ko'ra, algoritmlar bizning fikrlash jarayonlarimizni asta-sekinlik bilan passivlashtirishi mumkin. Bu holat, odamlar o'zlarining qarorlarini va fikrlarini tashqi tizimlar tomonidan boshqarilishi mumkin bo'lgan tarzda shakllantirishga o'rganadi. Odamlar doimiy ravishda algoritmlar tomonidan tavsiya etilgan kontentni iste'mol qiladilar, bu esa o'z navbatida ular tanlagan variantlarning juda cheklangan doirasiga olib keladi. Foydalanuvchilar faqat algoritmlar tavsiyalariga tayanib, o'zlarini mustaqil ravishda yangi bilimlarni izlashdan mahrum bo'lishlari mumkin.

Algoritmlar faqat shaxsiy fikrlash jarayonlarimizga emas, balki ijtimoiy qarorlarimizga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Masalan, siyosat yoki iqtisodiyotga oid fikrlarimizni shakllantiruvchi axborot ham algoritmlar tomonidan boshqarilishi mumkin. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda yoki yangiliklar saytlarida faqat bir xil fikrni targ'ib qiluvchi kontentning ko'payishi odamlar orasida polarizatsiyani kuchaytiradi.

Sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan ta'lim jarayonida foydalanish ta'lim jarayonida rang-baranglik, qiziqarli kontent, noodatij dars uchun zamin bo'lishi mumkin. Bu esa o'quvchilarni dars jarayoniga diqqatini qaratib, samaradorlikning oshishiga zamin bo'ladi. Biroq, bu vositalarning to'g'ri va mas'uliyatli ishlatilishi o'quvchilarning psixologik mustaqilligi va shaxsiy tanlovlariga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Shuning uchun, sun'iy intellekt tizimlari o'quvchilarga erkin tanlov qilish imkoniyatlarini taqdim etish, ularning mas'uliyat hissini oshirish, va mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish zarur.

1. O'quvchilarda o'z qarorlarini qabul qilishda faol bo'lishga undash va o'z qarorlariga nisbatan mas'uliyatni hissini shakllantirish. Masalan sun'iy intellekt tizimlari orqali o'z shaxsiy muvaffaqiyatlarini kuzatib borish, o'z natijalarini tahlil qilishni o'rgatish;

2. O'quvchilarga turli xil tavsiyalar berish, lekin har bir tavsiyaning asosini tushuntirish. Masalan, o'quvchilarga ularning qiziqishlari, ehtiyojlari va o'qish maqsadlariga moslashgan tavsiyalarni keltirish, lekin shu bilan birga o'quvchini tanlov qilishda erkin qoldirish.

3. O'quvchilarga sun'iy intellekt vositalarining qanday ishlashini, ularning tavsiyalari qaysi asoslarda ishlab chiqilishini tushuntirish. Bu o'quvchilarni algoritmlar tomonidan berilgan tavsiyalarni tanqidiy baholashga o'rgatadi va mustaqil qaror qabul qilishni rivojlantiradi.

O'quvchilarga shaxsiy ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilgan tavsiyalar berish, qaror qabul qilishda ularga erkinlik berish, va o'z qarorlarini tahlil qilishga undash – bu jarayonlarning barchasi o'quvchilarning rivojlanishiga va ta'limdagi muvaffaqiyatlariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt vositalari orqali o'quvchilarga o'z natijalarini kuzatib borish, tahlil qilish va o'zgarishlarni qabul qilish imkoniyatini yaratish ularning o'qish jarayoniga yanada faol yondashishiga yordam beradi.

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The Challenges of Using Augmented Reality in English Classrooms

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Abstract

This article explores the potential and challenges of implementing Augmented Reality (AR) in English classrooms. While AR offers opportunities for interactive, immersive learning experiences, its use in language education, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) settings, presents unique challenges. These challenges range from technological barriers, teacher readiness, and student engagement, to the practicalities of integrating AR within existing curricula. This study draws upon relevant literature and real-world examples to analyze these obstacles and suggests strategies for overcoming them.

Key words: Augmented Reality, English classrooms, technology in education, language learning, challenges, digital pedagogy.

Аннотация

В этой статье исследуются потенциал и проблемы внедрения дополненной реальности (AR) в классах английского языка. Хотя AR предлагает возможности для интерактивного, захватывающего обучения, его использование в языковом образовании, особенно в условиях английского как иностранного (EFL), представляет собой уникальные проблемы. Эти проблемы варьируются от технологических барьеров, готовности учителей и вовлеченности учащихся до практических аспектов интеграции AR в существующие учебные программы. Это исследование опирается на соответствующую литературу и примеры из реальной жизни для анализа этих препятствий и предлагает стратегии их преодоления.

Ключевые слова: Дополненная реальность, уроки английского языка, технологии в образовании, изучение языка, проблемы, цифровая педагогика.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola ingliz tili sinflarida kengaytirilgan haqiqatni (AR) joriy etish imkoniyatlari va muammolarini o'rganadi. AR interaktiv, immersiv o'rganish imkoniyatlarini taqdim etsa-da, undan til ta'limida, xususan, ingliz tilida chet tili (EFL) sifatida foydalanish o'ziga xos muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bu qiyinchiliklar texnologik to'siqlar, o'qituvchilarning tayyorgarligi va o'quvchilarning faolligidan tortib, mavjud o'quv dasturlariga ARni integratsiyalashning amaliy jihatlari gacha o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu tadqiqot ushbu to'siqlarni tahlil qilish uchun tegishli adabiyotlar va real dunyo misollariga tayanadi va ularni bartaraf etish strategiyalarini taklif qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kengaytirilgan reallik, ingliz tili sinflari, ta'limdagi texnologiya, til o'rganish, muammolar, raqamli pedagogika.

Introduction

Augmented Reality (AR) represents a significant development in educational technology, offering the potential to transform traditional learning environments into interactive spaces. AR integrates digital information, such as images, videos, and 3D models, into the physical world, providing students with new ways to engage with content. While AR has been widely discussed in STEM fields, its application in English classrooms, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) or English as a Second Language (ESL) contexts, is gaining attention.

However, despite its potential, there are considerable challenges that limit its effective use in English education. This article will examine the technical, pedagogical, and social challenges of using AR in English classrooms and propose potential solutions for overcoming these obstacles.

Methodology

This article adopts a mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative analysis of existing literature and case studies on AR in education. The study evaluates a variety of sources, including empirical research, theoretical discussions, and reports on AR pilot projects in educational settings. In addition to literature review, the study draws from expert interviews with teachers who have used AR in language classrooms to gather insights on practical challenges.

Literature Review:

A review of academic journals, conference proceedings, and books related to AR in education provides the foundation for understanding the technology's application in language learning. Specific attention is given to research in English language teaching (ELT) and educational technology.

Case Studies:

Several case studies from AR pilot programs in schools and universities are used to illustrate the real-world challenges of AR adoption in English classrooms. These examples are analyzed for common trends and challenges in AR

implementation.

Expert Interviews:

To add a practical perspective, interviews with English teachers who have integrated AR into their teaching are conducted. These interviews provide first-hand insights into the technical, pedagogical, and logistical challenges of using AR in the classroom.

Discussion

Technological Barriers

One of the most significant challenges in using AR in English classrooms is the technological barrier. The hardware required for AR, such as smartphones, tablets, or AR headsets, is not always readily available, especially in underfunded schools or regions with limited access to digital tools. Even when the devices are available, students and teachers often face connectivity issues, device compatibility problems, and software limitations.

Furthermore, the development of AR content tailored specifically for English learning is still in its infancy. Most AR applications focus on general education or STEM fields, leaving a gap in specialized resources for English language acquisition. Developing or adapting AR materials for specific language skills, such as grammar, pronunciation, or vocabulary acquisition, remains a challenge.

Teacher Readiness and Training

Another obstacle to AR integration is the readiness of teachers to use this technology. Many English teachers, particularly those with limited experience in using educational technology, feel unprepared to incorporate AR into their lesson plans. Teacher training programs often lag behind technological advancements, leaving educators with little knowledge of how to leverage AR effectively in the classroom.

There is also a pedagogical concern. AR is an innovative tool, but its success depends on how it is incorporated into existing teaching strategies. Teachers must learn not only how to use the technology but also how to design AR-based activities that align with learning outcomes. Without proper training, AR risks becoming a gimmick rather than a meaningful educational tool.

Student Engagement

While AR is often promoted as a means of enhancing student engagement, its novelty can sometimes wear off quickly. English classrooms, particularly in EFL settings, require sustained attention and repetition to build language proficiency. There is a risk that students may become distracted by the technology itself rather than focusing on the language-learning objectives.

Moreover, AR can sometimes overwhelm students, especially those who struggle with basic technological skills. If the use of AR becomes too complex, students may disengage or become frustrated, which can hinder their language learning

progress.

Curriculum Integration

Integrating AR into English curricula presents additional challenges. Most English curricula are designed around traditional teaching methods, with set textbooks and structured lesson plans. Incorporating AR requires flexibility and creativity, as teachers must find ways to embed AR activities within these constraints. Additionally, there may be resistance from school administrators who are hesitant to disrupt established curricula or invest in new technologies without clear evidence of improved outcomes.

Conclusion

While AR holds promise for enriching English language learning by providing interactive, immersive experiences, its implementation in classrooms is fraught with challenges. Technological barriers, such as hardware limitations and content availability, hinder widespread adoption, particularly in less affluent schools. Teachers face significant obstacles in terms of training and pedagogical adaptation, while students may either disengage or struggle to integrate the technology into their learning routines.

Despite these challenges, AR has the potential to revolutionize language learning if implemented thoughtfully. Schools must invest in teacher training and infrastructure, while curriculum developers should work closely with AR designers to create language-specific applications. As educational technology evolves, overcoming these challenges will be key to unlocking AR's potential in English classrooms.

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**TIL O‘QITISHNING IJTIMOIIY-GUMANITAR
JHATLARI**

**SOCIO-HUMANITARIAN ASPECTS OF LANGUAGE
TEACHING**

**СОЦИАЛЬНО-ГУМАНИТАРНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ
ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЯЗЫКОВ**

Teaching Writing to Non-Professional Students at Institutions: A Scientific Approach

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Abstract

There are particular difficulties when teaching writing to non-professional pupils in educational settings. These students need specialized coaching to help them build useful writing abilities that improve academic and professional communication, as they frequently choose fields that do not primarily focus on writing. In order to effectively teach writing to non-professional students, this study looks at pedagogical methodologies based on student-centered learning approaches, cognitive learning theories, and technological integration. Writing teaching can better meet the requirements of students in a variety of subject areas by emphasizing clarity, coherence, and relevance. This will promote academic success and the development of more comprehensive communicative skills.

Keywords: Cognitive Load Theory, constructivist approach, curriculum, writing tools, scaffolding, genre-specific writing.

Annotatsiya

Akademik muassasalarda yozishni o'rgatish, ayniqsa yozuvchilik bo'yicha mutaxassis bo'lmagan talabalarga dars berish, o'ziga xos muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bu talabalar odatda yozuv asosiy o'rin tutmaydigan sohalarida tahsil olishadi va ularga akademik hamda kasbiy muloqotda foydali bo'lgan amaliy yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun moslashtirilgan ta'lim zarur. Ushbu tadqiqot kognitiv o'qitish nazariyalari, talabaga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlar hamda zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo'llash asosida samarali yozuv darslarini o'rgatish strategiyalarini tahlil qiladi. Aniqlik, izchillik va mazmuniy dolzarblikni markazga qo'ygan holda yozuvni o'qitish yondashuvlari turli sohalarida tahsil olayotgan talabalar ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilishi mumkin, bu esa ularning akademik muvaffaqiyati va umumiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kognitiv yuklama nazariyasi, konstruktivistik yondashuv, o'quv dasturi, yozuv vositalari, bosqichma-bosqich o'rgatish, janrga xos yozuv.

Аннотация

Обучение письму студентов, не являющихся специалистами в этой области, в академических учреждениях представляет собой определённые трудности. Эти студенты, как правило, обучаются на факультетах, где письмо не занимает центральное место, и нуждаются в адаптированных методиках, способствующих развитию практических навыков письменной речи для успешной академической и профессиональной коммуникации. В данном исследовании рассматриваются педагогические стратегии, основанные на когнитивных теориях обучения, студентоцентрированном подходе и интеграции технологий для эффективного преподавания письма. Упор на ясность, логичность и актуальность позволяет адаптировать преподавание письма под потребности студентов различных дисциплин, способствуя их академическому успеху и развитию широких коммуникативных навыков.

Ключевые слова: теория когнитивной нагрузки, конструктивистский подход, учебный план, инструменты письма, поэтапное обучение, жанровое письмо.

Introduction

Students outside of the humanities and social sciences frequently receive little systematic instruction in writing, despite the fact that it is a crucial ability needed in all academic fields. Students in non-professional fields, like business, engineering, and science, usually struggle with professional and academic writing. For these students, writing is not a goal unto itself, but a means of disseminating professional and technical knowledge. Teachers encounter several obstacles when instructing these pupils in writing, such as low motivation, insufficient writing experience, and trouble adhering to genre-specific norms. Their needs might not be met by traditional writing teaching, so pedagogical adjustments are required to enhance learning results. This essay examines methods to deal with these issues that are based on educational theories and techniques.

Methods

This study employs a multidisciplinary approach informed by key educational theories:

1. Cognitive Load Theory (CLT): According to CLT, working memory's cognitive demands have an impact on learning. Learning can be made easier for non-professional students by reducing cognitive overload through the simplification of writing assignments and the use of scaffolding in instruction.

2. Constructivist Learning: Active learning via experience and introspection is emphasized by Vygotsky's constructivist philosophy. Engagement and retention are increased when writing training is connected to students' academic and professional experiences.

3. Genre Theory: This theory emphasizes the social context of writing and has its roots in Bakhtin's writing. Students can more successfully negotiate professional communication if they are aware of the rules of particular genres, such as lab reports or business proposals.

Study Design

With the help of case studies and an examination of instructional tactics used in non-professional fields, the study includes a qualitative overview of current pedagogical approaches for teaching writing.

Gathering and Analyzing Data

Information was obtained from the following sources: - Scholarly works on teaching writing.

- Observations in non-professional subjects' classrooms.

Surveys of teachers and students are used to pinpoint important issues and successful teaching methods.

Findings

Obstacles Non-Professional Students Face

1. Lack of Motivation: Students frequently consider writing to be less important than their main academic objectives.
2. Genre-Specific Conventions: It can be difficult to become proficient in some writing formats, such as business memos or technical reports.
3. Limited Writing Practice: Technical skills are frequently given precedence over writing in STEM-focused programs, which results in a lack of communication skills.
4. Cognitive Overload: Simultaneously learning technical content and new writing strategies overwhelms students.
5. Language Barriers: Non-native speakers face additional challenges in expressing technical ideas clearly.

Pedagogical Approaches

1. Writing Integration into the Curriculum: Students are encouraged to see writing as a vital learning tool when writing assignments are incorporated into foundational courses.
2. Genre-Based Instruction: Students gain useful abilities for professional communication by learning the conventions of particular genres.
3. Scaffolding and Sequencing Tasks: Dividing assignments into more manageable chunks can boost confidence and lessen cognitive stress.
4. Peer review and collaborative writing: Peer review encourages participation and introspection.
5. Technology Use: Writing is made easier and less stressful with the use of tools like collaboration platforms, citation managers, and grammar checkers.

Assessment Strategies

Writing ability and content knowledge are balanced in an effective assessment. Students benefit from rubrics that make clear the standards for communication quality and technical accuracy. Formative feedback encourages continuous development and reduces writing-related anxiety.

Discussion

Teaching writing to non-professional students demands addressing their particular needs through innovative teaching methodologies. By utilizing cognitive load theory, instructors can lower the difficulty of writing tasks and promote progressive learning. While genre-based education gives students useful skills for real-world applications, constructivist methods promote active engagement. Institutional issues must be resolved, nevertheless, such as the lack of writing pedagogy training among faculty members. Providing educators with resources and support to integrate writing teaching into non-professional disciplines is vital. Furthermore, utilizing technology can fill holes in traditional writing education. Future study could include

longitudinal studies to investigate the influence of these tactics on students' academic and professional achievement.

Conclusion

Teaching writing to non-professional students is critical for their academic and professional development. Educators can address these pupils' issues by including writing into the curriculum, stressing genre-specific conventions, and utilizing technology. Institutions must stress cross-disciplinary communication abilities in order to prepare students for the needs of today's workforce.

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The Process Approach to Teaching Vocabulary: Theoretical Foundations and Practical Implications

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ANNOTATION

The process approach to teaching vocabulary is explained in this article with particular emphasis on its theoretical basis and practical usage in language instruction. It explains through active involvement, contextualized input, and reflection how the process approach enables significant learning, learner autonomy, and retention. Implementation challenges are examined and pragmatic solutions are explored. The importance of the method in enhancing students' vocabulary acquisition and communicative ability is emphasized in the last words of the article.

KEYWORDS

Vocabulary acquisition, process approach, active learning, contextualization, learner autonomy, reflection, language teaching methodology.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada soʻz boʻyligini oʻqitishda jarayon yondashuvi nazariy asoslari va amaliy qoʻllanilishi asosida tushuntirilgan. Unda faol ishtirok, kontekstual materiallar va refleksiya orqali bu yondashuv qanday qilib mazmunli oʻrganish, oʻquvchi mustaqilligi va eslab qolishni taʼminlashi bayon etiladi. Amaliyotda duch kelinadigan muammolar tahlil qilinib, ular uchun amaliy yechimlar taklif etilgan. Maqolaning yakunida bu uslub talabalarning soʻz boʻyligini kengaytirish va muloqot qobiliyatini oshirishdagi ahamiyati alohida taʼkidlanadi.

Kalit soʻzlar

Lugʻat boʻyligini oshirish, jarayon yondashuvi, faollashtirilgan oʻqitish, kontekstualizatsiya, oʻquvchi mustaqilligi, aks ettirish, til oʻqitish metodologiyasi.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается процессуальный подход к обучению лексике с особым акцентом на его теоретические основы и практическое применение в преподавании языка. Объясняется, как через активное участие, контекстуализированный материал и рефлексию данный подход способствует значимому обучению, автономии учащихся и лучшему запоминанию. Рассматриваются сложности внедрения и предлагаются практические решения. В заключение подчеркивается важность данного метода для расширения словарного запаса и развития коммуникативных навыков студентов.

Ключевые слова

Освоение словарного запаса, процессуальный подход, активное обучение, контекстуализация, автономия учащихся, рефлексия, методика преподавания языка.

INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary knowledge has been traditionally accepted as one of the fundamental components of language proficiency, the foundation upon which all the language skills—speaking, listening, reading, and writing—are built. Without a proper vocabulary, students cannot express their ideas with clarity or comprehend others with accuracy. Vocabulary instruction has long been founded on mere memorization and repetitive drilling, methods that could only lead to superficial learning and rapid forgetting. In recent decades, however, language instruction has been shifting towards methodologies that assign value to both deeper understanding and practical use of words. The process approach to vocabulary teaching is one such newer methodology, demanding learner involvement through multiple phases of vocabulary learning. Instead of considering vocabulary learning as an event or a simple activity of memorizing lists of words, the process view invites learners to encounter new words multiple times in varied contexts, to use them actively, and to think about their meaning. This article examines the theoretical assumptions underlying this approach and considers classroom practices in language teaching through which it can be realized, with the ultimate goal of facilitating more effective and durable vocabulary learning.

The Process Approach: Theoretical Foundations

The process approach to vocabulary teaching is supported by a wide range of cognitive psychological theories and sociocultural theories that emphasize learning, all of which highlight active learner engagement, meaningful input, and reflective practice. These theories provide a clear rationale for why the process approach is effective in bringing about deeper vocabulary learning. One of the strongest theoretical foundations of the process approach is constructivist learning theory, specifically Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. Vygotsky (1978) emphasized that learning is a social process in which learners construct new knowledge through interactions with more knowledgeable others, such as teachers or peers. This would mean that vocabulary learning is not simply an exercise in memorizing the meaning of words but negotiating and constructing meanings socially. As learners talk, share ideas, and clarify meanings with one another, they internalize vocabulary more deeply than they would through isolated memorization. Social interaction enhances cognitive development and allows learners to connect new words to their existing knowledge, a prerequisite for meaningful learning.

Input Hypothesis and Comprehensible Input

Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1982) provides another critical insight into how vocabulary is acquired. Krashen argued that language acquisition occurs most effectively when learners receive input that is just beyond their current level of competence, often described as "i+1." In vocabulary teaching, this translates to exposing learners to new words within contexts that allow them to infer meaning without needing direct translation. This comprehensible input should be rich, varied, and meaningful, enabling learners to understand the gist of messages while gradually building their vocabulary knowledge. The process approach aligns closely with this idea by presenting new words embedded in authentic texts or communicative situations, supporting learners in making natural, context-based connections to new vocabulary. The Depth of Processing theory, proposed by Craik and Lockhart (1972), further explains why the process approach facilitates better retention of vocabulary. According to this theory, information processed at a deeper semantic level—such as through meaningful use, association with prior knowledge, or contextual elaboration—is more likely to be remembered than information processed superficially. The process approach encourages learners to engage deeply with vocabulary by using words in various meaningful tasks, relating them to personal experiences, comparing them with synonyms or antonyms, and reflecting on their nuances. This multi-layered engagement strengthens memory traces and promotes long-term retention. Additionally, cognitive load theory underlines the importance of managing the amount and difficulty of information learners process at once. Introducing too many new words simultaneously or expecting immediate mastery can overwhelm learners' working memory, hindering learning. The process approach addresses this by breaking

vocabulary learning into manageable stages and promoting spaced repetition—re-exposing learners to words over time in different contexts. This gradual, repeated exposure supports the transfer of vocabulary from short-term to long-term memory, facilitating more stable acquisition.

Practical Applications of the Process Approach

Implementing the process approach in language classrooms requires creating rich learning environments where vocabulary is not just introduced but explored, practiced, and internalized over time. This approach moves beyond memorizing word lists to involve learners actively and meaningfully at every stage of vocabulary learning. One of the main practical strategies of the process approach is to introduce vocabulary within authentic, meaningful contexts. Instead of presenting isolated words with dictionary definitions, teachers embed new vocabulary in stories, dialogues, articles, or multimedia materials that mirror real-life communication. This contextualization enables learners to guess meanings based on surrounding text or situation, encouraging active inference and enhancing comprehension. For example, presenting the word “bargain” in a dialogue about shopping allows learners to understand its connotations and use naturally. Such exposure aligns with Krashen’s Input Hypothesis and supports learners’ ability to transfer vocabulary knowledge to real communication.

Active Production: Speaking and Writing

Vocabulary becomes firmly rooted in learners’ minds when they use it actively. The process approach emphasizes opportunities for learners to speak and write using new vocabulary, transforming passive recognition into active command. Classroom activities such as role-plays, debates, presentations, and storytelling allow learners to practice vocabulary in communicative settings, while writing tasks like journals, essays, or creative stories encourage deeper engagement with word meanings and usage. Active production not only reinforces retention but also builds learners’ confidence and fluency.

Reflection and Learner Autonomy

The process approach encourages students to take responsibility for learning their vocabulary through reflective practice. Maintaining vocabulary notebooks or online journals where students record new words, their meanings, example sentences, collocations, and personal comments enables metacognition—thinking about thinking.

Reflective activities, such as review and revision of word lists, sorting words, or self-practice, encourage learner awareness and motivation. Such a feeling of autonomy allows learners to set goals, monitor progress, and implement strategies that suit their individual needs. Cooperative learning is another support for the process approach. Group tasks such as peer teaching, vocabulary games, brainstorming, and group storytelling engage learners to negotiate meaning, question, and correct each

other's mistakes. Social interaction in this way mimics the use of language in natural settings, thus making vocabulary learning more active and meaningful. It also addresses Vygotsky's sociocultural theory that highlights social mediation of cognition. Technology use contributes to the process approach by creating flexible and personalized practice environments. Spaced repetition programs are used by computer flashcard software like Quizlet or Anki to optimize vocabulary review, while online games and quizzes and language learning sites provide interactive and stimulating practice arenas. Technology also allows students to apply vocabulary tools outside the classroom, extending opportunities for learning and accommodating multiple learning styles.

Challenges in Implementing the Process Approach

Though very valuable, the process approach has real-world practical constraints that need to be taken into consideration by the teacher. The primary constraint is the amount of time involved. As the approach involves multiple stages—introduction, contextualization, active use, reflection, and review—the process approach does take up more class time than traditional memorization-based teaching. Teachers have to carefully organize lessons to balance curricular objectives against the increased participation the process approach involves. The second difficulty is learner resistance. Those students accustomed to passive learning and memorization by repetition will necessarily be uneasy or annoyed with active learning activities that include speaking, writing, and reflection. Resistance may be countered by gradual integration of process activities, clear explanation of their benefits, and steady encouragement. Classroom management is also challenging. Group work and interactive activities require effective classroom management skills to ensure effective participation and prevent distraction. Teachers have to design well-structured activities with clear instructions and roles to guarantee student attention and maximize participation. When used properly, the process approach produces notable improvements in learners' vocabulary understanding and language ability. Studies indicate that learners develop stronger retention and recall abilities because they meet vocabulary on multiple cognitive levels and in various contexts. The approach also boosts learners' confidence and motivation by promoting autonomy and active involvement. Learners further develop communicative competence because they can utilize vocabulary more effectively and appropriately to use in speech and writing. Such outcomes bring about general language ability and lead to preparing learners for real communication.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the process approach to vocabulary teaching offers a learner-centered, whole-language alternative to more conventional methods. Founded on sound theoretical foundations in the guise of constructivism, input hypothesis, and cognitive theory, it enables rich, deep vocabulary learning through contextualized

exposure, active use, reflection, and learner control. Although it is slower and more time-consuming, the benefits of the process in fostering long-term vocabulary growth and communicative ability make it highly effective in modern language instruction. By addressing problems with sensitivity and utilizing technology and cooperative techniques, teachers can successfully implement the process approach to promote successful and long-term vocabulary growth.

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Integrating Technology into Vocabulary Instruction in EFL Classrooms

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Annotation. This article discovers the integration of technology into vocabulary teaching in English for Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. It examines the influence of digital tools such as mobile applications, online games, learning management systems (LMS) and interactive multimedia resources on the enhancement of vocabulary acquisition, retention and learner motivation. Drawing on recent research and pedagogical practices, this article discusses the positive outcomes offered by technology-enhanced learning and teaching, considering learner autonomy, personalized instruction and real-time feedback. Challenges which might be faced by educators will be also considered, such as digital literacy gaps and technological limitations in certain educational contexts.

Keywords: Vocabulary instruction, EFL classrooms, educational technology, digital tools, learner autonomy, motivation, vocabulary acquisition, Learning management systems (LMS).

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается интеграция технологий в преподавание лексики в классах английского языка как иностранного (EFL). Анализируется влияние цифровых инструментов, таких как мобильные приложения, онлайн-игры, системы управления обучением (LMS) и интерактивные мультимедийные ресурсы, на улучшение усвоения, запоминания лексики и мотивации обучающихся. Основываясь на современных исследованиях и педагогической практике, в статье обсуждаются положительные результаты, которые предлагает обучение с использованием технологий, включая развитие автономии учащихся, персонализированное обучение и обратную связь в реальном времени. Также рассматриваются возможные проблемы, с которыми могут столкнуться преподаватели, такие как недостаточный уровень цифровой грамотности и технологические ограничения в отдельных образовательных контекстах.

Ключевые слова: Обучение лексике, EFL классы, образовательные технологии, цифровые инструменты, автономия обучающихся, мотивация, усвоение лексики, системы управления обучением (LMS).

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tili sifatida ingliz tili (EFL) sinflarida lug'at o'qitish jarayoniga texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish masalasi o'rganiladi. Mobil ilovalar, onlayn o'yinlar, o'quv jarayonini boshqarish tizimlari (LMS) va interaktiv multimedia vositalari kabi raqamli vositalarning lug'atni o'zlashtirish, eslab qolish va o'quvchilarni rag'batlantirishga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlar va pedagogik tajribalarga tayangan holda, maqolada texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda ta'limning ijobiy jihatlari — o'quvchilarning mustaqil ta'lim olish imkoniyati, shaxsiylashtirilgan yondashuv va real vaqt rejimidagi fikr-mulohazalar muhokama qilinadi. Shuningdek, ayrim ta'limiy sharoitlarda raqamli savodxonlikning pastligi va texnologik cheklovlar kabi muammolar ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Lug'at o'qitish, EFL sinflari, ta'lim texnologiyalari, raqamli vositalar, o'quvchi mustaqilligi, rag'batlantirish, lug'atni o'zlashtirish, o'quv jarayonini boshqarish tizimlari (LMS).

Technology has increasingly come to play a modern facilitating role in teaching and learning, particularly language teaching. In fact, vocabulary acquisition, interfacing as it does with the broader area of language ability, has profited immensely from the application of digital tools and resources. EFL teachers are thus gradually making a paradigm shift away from the traditional forms of rote memorization toward more dynamic, interactive, and learner-centered methods, presently nourished by technological innovations.

Mobile technologies have increasingly played their role in language learning, as emphasized by Godwin-Jones (2011) and Kukulska-Hulme & Shield (2008), having shown the possibilities in their research for mobile phones and tablets to offer on-demand vocabulary support, collaborative learning experiences, and flexible access to resources.⁶² CALL – computer-assessed language learning – environments could also support vocabulary development through multimedia input and interaction, according to Chapelle (2001).⁶³

In addition to the support for explicit vocabulary instruction through structured content delivery, tracking of learner content, and immediate feedback, learning management systems such as Moodle, Edmodo, and Google Classroom provide further facilities (Burston, 2015).⁶⁴ The above-mentioned systems enable teachers to add multimedia materials and track learner's progress, facilitating more productive and guided instruction.

⁶² Kukulska-Hulme, A., Shield, L. An overview of mobile assisted language learning: From content delivery to supported collaboration and interaction // *ReCALL*. 2008. Vol. 20, No. 3. P. 271–289.

⁶³ Chapelle, C. A. *Computer applications in second language acquisition: Foundations for teaching, testing and research*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001. 225 p.

⁶⁴ Burston, J. Twenty years of MALL project implementation: A meta-analysis of learning outcomes // *ReCALL*. 2015. Vol. 27, No. 1. P. 4–20.

Benefits of technology integration in vocabulary teaching

Technology enables one to incorporate interactive and multimodal input-in the realm of diverse learning styles. With the help of tools such as Quizlet, Memrise, Anki, the learner can be cast against vocabulary-building activities, whether games, spaced repetition, or self-made flashcards. Learner autonomy is supported by these types of sites-that is, they allow learners to create their own goals, to keep track of progress, and to schedule their own time for review.

Then again, multimedia programs (i.e., videos, animations, podcasts) put words before the learners in their contexts, which increases retention and usability. For instance, a video with subtitles exposes learners to natural use, pronunciation, and collocations in genuine contexts. Digital stories and vocabulary games help to further entertain and meaningfully engage learners.

Practical strategies for classroom integration

Integration of technology in vocabulary teaching needs a considered approach to harmonize technological ability and learning objectives. Educators must themselves view technology as an enhancement, in contrast to a distraction, of the learning process. Several realistic and elaborate options that EFL teachers can invoke in varying educational scenarios are given below:

1. Blended Learning Approaches

- Mix in-person teaching with digital tools for vocabulary reinforcement in and out of the classroom.
- Upload vocabulary lists, quizzes, and video explanations on Google Classroom or any other LMS such as Moodle or Edmodo, on a weekly basis.
- Consider giving students digital homework such as matching exercises or sentence creation with vocabulary apps.
- Use flipped teaching techniques by sharing vocabulary videos, interactive readings, etc., for students to prepare prior to class.

2. Mobile and Web-Based Apps

- Encourage learners to use vocabulary learning apps that fit their level and interests.
- With Quizlet, Memrise, and WordUp, learners can make and share flashcard sets.
- SRS will maintain a student's longer retention of newly learned words.
- Use gamification to nurture learners' motivation to maintain and practice their new vocabulary in-app.

3. Digital Storytelling and Creative Tasks

- Students create digital content with the target vocabulary to build language and digital skills simultaneously.

- Use Canva, Adobe Express, or Storybird to create posters, comics, or short stories using the new vocabulary.
- As a cluster activity, students create videos, podcasts, or slideshows using thematic vocabulary (e.g., travel, food, environment).

These kinds of projects nurture creativity, collaboration, and contextualized word use.

Challenges and considerations

There remain some important challenges and considerations regarding the integration of technology into vocabulary instruction. Limited access to digital devices with a good internet connection represents one important challenge, especially in the case of rural or under-resourced schools. Without a good infrastructure, the effective implementation of online tools remains questionable. Furthermore, students are split between those with digital literacy skills and those without—the latter remain at the bottom of the digital divide in the classroom. Some teachers may feel ill-prepared or untrained in using educational technology, especially those who have traditionally used standard methods. This lack of proper training often results in instructors rendering the digital tools superficially or ineffectively.

Also, not all technological tools are sound from a pedagogical standpoint; some such applications promote rote memorization at the expense of deeper understanding and would therefore become poorly aligned with goals of the curriculum. The teachers hence must make a careful evaluation in terms of the quality and relevance of all tech content that they intend to employ. Time management becomes the next challenge; technology-based instruction is time-consuming to prepare and implement, occasionally to the detriment of actual teaching. Providing relevant feedback is another issue, especially in large classrooms, where an automated system may fail to consider important contextual nuances. Specifically, a school should fund its infrastructure and professional development programs, while teachers should cautiously and mindfully approach the integration of technology to support, rather than interfere with, vocabulary learning.

In conclusion, technology is no longer viewed as luxury for teaching methodology but rather as a means to construct 21st century teaching and learning. The presence of digital tools, LMSs, and interactive resources enhances student engagement and provides avenues for personalized and effective learning. As the digital landscape changes, educators will have to adapt by capitalizing upon new technologies that have the potential to better teaching and learning. Such changes will also require ongoing professional development for teachers and their institutions to support these changes. Schools and colleges that can create an environment for meaningful integration of technology will thereby better prepare students for a 21st century challenge and better equip them with skills that would enable them to thrive in

a society that is largely digital. All the while, some drawbacks such as the uneven distribution of digital resources and the undue reliance on technology must be kept in check so that education innovation can take the best of both worlds.

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The Role of Learner Autonomy in Effective Vocabulary Acquisition

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Annotation. This article discovers the importance of learner autonomy in effective vocabulary learning among students and how it creates an opportunity to acquire vocabulary independently outside the classroom. It emphasizes the correlation between independent learning strategies, self-assessment, personal responsibility and enhanced vocabulary retention and usage. The article also provides related results from recent research and draws on examples to illustrate how fostering learner autonomy can lead to long-term success in language learning process.

Keywords: Learner autonomy, vocabulary acquisition, self-directed learning, language learning strategies, motivation, retention.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается важность автономии учащихся в эффективном усвоении словарного запаса и то, как она создает возможности для самостоятельного изучения лексики вне классной комнаты. Подчеркивается взаимосвязь между стратегиями самостоятельного обучения, самооценкой, личной ответственностью и улучшением запоминания и использования лексики. Также приводятся результаты недавних исследований и примеры, демонстрирующие, как развитие автономии учащихся может привести к долгосрочному успеху в процессе изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: Автономия учащегося, усвоение лексики, самостоятельное обучение, стратегии изучения языка, мотивация, запоминание.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'quvchi mustaqilligining lug'atni samarali o'zlashtirishdagi o'rni tahlil qiladi. Unda o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'rganish strategiyalari, o'z-o'zini baholash va shaxsiy mas'uliyati bilan lug'atni eslab qolish va qo'llash darajasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik yoritiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada so'nggi tadqiqotlar natijalari hamda amaliy misollar orqali mustaqillikni

rivojlantirish til o'rganish jarayonida uzoq muddatli muvaffaqiyatga qanday olib kelishi ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'quvchi mustaqilligi, lug'atni o'zlashtirish, mustaqil o'rganish, til o'rganish strategiyalari, motivatsiya, eslab qolish.

Vocabulary acquisition is essential for proficiency and fluency in any language. Earlier, much of the instruction was teacher-centered; thus, the teacher held the authority for deciding what content is taught, the pace of delivery, or the teaching strategies to be employed. In contrast, recent research has focused more on the learner's ability to have autonomous control over his or her learning processes. This definitely applies to vocabulary learning, as the exercising of learner autonomy could increase motivation, retention, and use of new vocabulary by learners on their own, both inside and outside the classroom.

Learner autonomy is the capacity of learners to make decisions on their individual learning processes. This may involve setting learning goals, choosing a learning strategy, and even evaluating one's progress from time to time, according to Benson (2011).⁶⁵ Autonomy concerning vocabulary learning means learners do not rely solely on the teacher, but are also engaged in different activities designed to expand and retain their lexical knowledge independently. With the growing use of technology, learner autonomy is becoming even more important, as it provides students with access to a range of digital resources and avenues for practicing vocabulary in ways that are contingent on their individual needs and schedules.

The role of Learner Autonomy in Vocabulary Learning

Autonomy in vocabulary learning enables learners to actively participate in when and how new words are encountered in their lives. Thus, independent strategies like extensive reading, using flashcards, and vocabulary apps allow learners to see the new words almost anywhere, allowing for their deeper understanding and/or retention. Once learners take ownership of the vocabulary acquisition process, they typically find meaningful contexts where they can practice vocabulary in communication.

Studies have shown that vocabulary learners who engage actively in self-directed vocabulary acquisition processes retain and utilize new words to a much greater extent (Lai, 2015).⁶⁶ Self-directed learners dictate their own vocabulary-learning process through choosing words that maintain relevance to their personal interests or academic and professional goals. This relevance acts as a motivator because learners become emotionally involved in the learning material and thus see the immediate value of learning the new vocabulary.

⁶⁵ Benson, P. (2011). **Teaching and researching autonomy in language learning** (2nd ed.). Harlow: Longman.

⁶⁶ Lai, C. (2015). **Learner autonomy in language learning: A critical review.** *Language Teaching Research*, 19(4), p. 417–442.

Furthermore, autonomous learners tend to choose the widest variety of strategies to increase their vocabulary acquisition. These include using spaced repetition techniques (smartphone apps like Anki or Memrise), contextual learning (from reading books, listening to podcasts, or watching movies), or self-testing. The use of self-assessment strategies, such as vocabulary notebooks or online quizzes, helps students to identify and track areas of progress and areas needing improvement in their vocabulary.

Pedagogical Implications

The value of autonomy in learners in relation to vocabulary acquisition does not mean that teachers should lose control of the learning process. Rather, the creation of an autonomous environment is of great importance. This includes providing the right level of support for the students, sometimes referred to as scaffolding, which helps learners gradually take responsibility for their own learning. Teachers can assist students in formulating sound learning strategies, setting attainable learning milestones, and reflecting on their achievements. Some autonomy supportive activities are project-based learning, cooperative learning, and working with technological resources. Students can also be supported to design their individual vocabulary learning projects such as vocabulary blogs, personal word banks, or digital flashcards. Quizlet, Duolingo, and Memrise are some of the online resources for vocabulary practice which are learner-centric, interactive and gamified, resulting in better retention among learners. In addition, teachers can use meta-cognitive tools such as vocabulary journals or self-evaluating rubrics that prompted learners to think about the process of learning as a way to foster autonomy.

Challenges in Promoting Learner Autonomy

A key advantage of autonomy in learning lies in vocabulary acquisition; however, challenges arise from the implementation of self-guided learning in educational systems with a traditional framework. A great number of students are used to guided instructions and, hence, have a problem being responsible for their own learning. Some learners may be unskilled regarding how to participate in self-directed learning, while others have little motivation to put in extra work outside class hours.

In addition, there are some learners who have cultural background considerations. In some cultures, the educator is regarded as the most authoritative person in the class; thus, the idea of learner-centered teaching may be new and uncomfortable for both the learners and the teachers. As a result, autonomy of learners should be introduced gradually. Educators need to design smaller and simpler strategies to promote autonomy, such as allowing students to choose what they would like to do in the classroom or enabling them to determine personal vocabulary learning objectives. Eventually, students will learn to become fully autonomous over their vocabulary learning processes.

The Importance of Motivation in Learner Autonomy

Motivation is perhaps the most important element that cultivates learner autonomy. This phenomenon can be well understood in relation to a concept elaborated in one of the studies conducted by Deci & Ryan (2000), in the case where students are motivated by personal reasons, they tend to exert additional effort into autonomous learning activities.⁶⁷ It can, therefore, be understood that motivation allows the learner to appreciate the importance of improving their vocabulary and understand the need to spend both time and effort in vocabulary learning. Motivation may be better encouraged if teachers set environments to show students the importance of vocabulary learning in relation to their personal goals. For instance, those students learning a foreign language for professional reasons may be further encouraged to learn vocabulary connected with their area of professional engagement. Also, rewarding students for accomplishing positive outcomes can be helpful in fostering motivation as well as commitment to self-directed learning.

In conclusion, the effectiveness of vocabulary acquisition relies profoundly on learner autonomy. Such autonomy enables students to not only learn new vocabulary but also retain and use it in relevant contexts. In combination with self-directed learning, motivation, and varied learning approaches, learners are better equipped to handle vocabulary acquisition on their own—inside and outside the classroom. Teachers are still needed, but instead of taking the lead, they need to assist learners as they learn the skills that will help them learn vocabulary independently for the rest of their lives. With changes in vocabulary teaching, the independence of students will always be cited as one of the most important approaches to effective vocabulary acquisition.

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TASK-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the significance of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in secondary schools. It focuses on how TBLT enhances communicative competence, develops problem-solving skills, and increases learner motivation. The article also presents key methods of implementing TBLT, examines research findings on its effectiveness, and highlights potential challenges with suggested solutions. Understanding TBLT equips language educators with effective strategies for engaging students and fostering meaningful language use.

Keywords: task-based learning, secondary education, communicative competence, language skills, motivation.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена изучению значения метода обучения иностранным языкам на основе выполнения заданий (TBLT) в средних школах. Рассматривается, как TBLT способствует развитию коммуникативной компетенции, навыков решения проблем и повышению мотивации учащихся. Приводятся основные методы реализации TBLT, результаты исследований его эффективности, а также возможные проблемы и их решения.

Ключевые слова: обучение на основе заданий, среднее образование, коммуникативная компетенция, языковые навыки, мотивация.

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqola o'rta maktablarda topshiriqlarga asoslangan chet tilini o'qitish (TBLT) usulining ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Unda TBLT o'quvchilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga, muammolarni hal qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga va o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyani oshirishga qanday ta'sir qilishi haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, TBLT ni amalga oshirish usullari, uning samaradorligi bo'yicha tadqiqot natijalari va duch kelinadigan muammolar va ularning echimlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: topshiriqqa asoslangan o'qitish, o'rta ta'lim, kommunikativ qobiliyat, til ko'nikmalari, motivatsiya.

Introduction. The increasing globalization and need for practical communication skills have emphasized the importance of innovative teaching methods in secondary schools. Among these methods, Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) stands out due to its learner-centered approach and emphasis on real-world language use. TBLT promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and collaboration, making it an effective methodology for the 21st-century classroom (Jackson, 2022).

Literary Analysis and Methodology. Task-Based Language Teaching is grounded in the communicative approach, but takes it a step further by organizing instruction around «tasks» instead of traditional grammar or vocabulary topics. According to Long (2016), a task is any activity where the target language is used by

the learner for a communicative purpose in order to achieve an outcome. This focus on authentic communication shifts the classroom dynamics fundamentally.

In TBLT, tasks are carefully selected to reflect real-world language use. Examples include planning a trip, conducting an interview, or writing a blog post. As noted by Ilyasova (2024), such activities enhance learners' abilities to use language functionally rather than mechanically.

Bakoev (2024) emphasizes the flexibility TBLT offers in tailoring language education to learner needs. TBLT tasks can be designed to target specific skills like speaking, listening, reading, and writing, often integrating multiple skills into one cohesive activity. This holistic development is crucial for effective secondary education.

Methodologically, TBLT consists of three primary stages:

1. Pre-task phase: The teacher introduces the topic, provides models, and ensures that learners understand the task requirements.

2. During-task phase: Students perform the task, often in pairs or groups, emphasizing fluency over accuracy.

3. Post-task phase: Students reflect on the task performance, engage in form-focused activities to correct errors, and expand their language awareness.

Khujakulov et al. (2024) highlight the importance of the teacher's role in scaffolding tasks and providing linguistic support without dominating the learning process. Effective scaffolding includes clarifying task procedures, offering useful expressions, and helping students manage their interaction patterns.

Moreover, the evaluation process in TBLT focuses more on performance-based assessment rather than traditional tests. As noted by Rasulqulova (2025), formative assessments, peer evaluations, and self-assessments are key tools for measuring students' communicative competence.

Challenges such as managing mixed-ability groups and large class sizes are acknowledged in the literature (Bakoev, 2024). Solutions involve careful task design, the use of differentiated instruction, and the incorporation of technology to facilitate collaborative work.

Ultimately, TBLT aligns language learning with cognitive and socio-cultural theories of education. It motivates students by making learning meaningful and contextually relevant, thus better preparing them for real-life language use.

In addition to the key phases of TBLT implementation, it is crucial to consider the theoretical frameworks that underpin the methodology. One important influence on TBLT is Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, which emphasizes the role of social interaction and scaffolding in language learning. According to this view, learners construct knowledge through collaboration with peers and teachers, making task-based approaches particularly effective (Jackson, 2022).

Furthermore, TBLT aligns closely with the principles of constructivism, where learners are active participants in their learning process. Tasks provide meaningful contexts in which students negotiate meaning, solve problems, and reflect on their language use, thus internalizing new knowledge more effectively (Long, 2016).

The methodology also benefits from insights drawn from the Interaction Hypothesis, which posits that negotiation of meaning during communicative interaction facilitates language development.

Results and Discussion. Research indicates that TBLT improves students' communicative competence, motivation, and confidence (Khujakulov et al., 2024). In secondary schools, the method encourages collaboration and contextual learning, making language acquisition more natural and effective.

However, TBLT also presents challenges: **Assessment Difficulties:** Traditional exams may not accurately measure communicative competence. **Resource Limitations:** Implementing authentic tasks requires materials and classroom settings that may not always be available. Solutions proposed by Rasulqulova (2025) include using simplified tasks when resources are limited and integrating formative assessment methods to better evaluate student progress.

Moreover, training teachers to design effective tasks and manage learner interaction is crucial for successful implementation.

Conclusion. Task-Based Language Teaching provides an effective, dynamic alternative to traditional language teaching methods in secondary schools. By emphasizing real-world communication and learner autonomy, TBLT prepares students for practical language use beyond the classroom. Despite its challenges, careful planning and adaptation can ensure that TBLT meets the needs of diverse student populations and contributes significantly to their language development.

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INGILIZ TILINI O'RGANISHDA O'QISH KO'NIKMALARINING AHAMIYATI VA O'QITUVCHILARNING O'QISHNI TUSHUNISHIDAGI ROLI

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ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganishda o'qish ko'nikmalarining ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi va o'qish tushunishini rivojlantirishda o'qituvchilarning rolini o'rganadi. O'qish ko'nikmalarini o'zlashtirish uchun yaxshi rejalashtirilgan o'qitish jarayonlarining ahamiyatini muhokama qiladi va o'quvchilarning barcha darajalari uchun o'qish ko'nikmalarini o'qitishning foydalarini yoritadi. Maqolada o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonidagi uchta asosiy bosqich: oldindan o'qish, o'qish jarayonida va o'qishdan keyin, har bir bosqichda maqsad va faoliyatlar tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, o'qish ko'nikmalarini o'qitishda o'qituvchilarning muhim roli muhokama qilinadi va intensiv va keng qamrovli o'qish amaliyotlari davomida ularning o'rni haqida fikrlar beriladi. Maqola, talabalar uchun o'qish qobiliyatini va tushunish ko'nikmalarini oshirishga yordam beradigan o'qitish tamoyillarini taqdim etish bilan yakunlanadi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: O'qish ko'nikmasi, strategiyalar, o'qitish va o'rganish bosqichlari, o'qituvchilarning o'qish ko'nikmasini o'qitishdagi roli, intensiv o'qish, keng qamrovli o'qish, o'qitish tamoyillari.

АННОТАЦИЯ. Данная статья подчеркивает важность навыков чтения при изучении английского языка как иностранного и исследует роль учителей в развитии понимания прочитанного. Обсуждается значимость хорошо спланированных учебных процессов для освоения навыков чтения и освещаются преимущества обучения навыкам чтения для учащихся всех уровней. В статье рассматриваются три основные стадии процесса обучения и обучения: предшествующее чтение, чтение и пост чтение, с объяснением целей и деятельности на каждой стадии. Также обсуждается важная роль учителей в обучении навыкам чтения и даются рекомендации относительно их места в процессе интенсивного и широкого чтения. Статья завершается представлением принципов обучения, которые помогают студентам развивать навыки чтения и понимания.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: навык чтения, стратегии, стадии обучения и усвоения, роль учителей в обучении навыкам чтения, интенсивное чтение, широкое чтение, принципы обучения.

ANNOTATION. This article emphasizes the importance of reading skills in learning English as a foreign language and explores the role of teachers in developing reading comprehension. It discusses the significance of well-planned teaching processes for mastering reading skills and highlights the benefits of teaching reading skills for students at all levels. The article outlines the three main phases in the teaching and learning process: pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading,

explaining the goals and activities for each phase. It also discusses the crucial role of teachers in teaching reading skills and offers insights into their role during intensive and extensive reading practices. The article concludes by presenting teaching principles that can help enhance students' reading abilities and comprehension skills.

KEYWORDS: reading skill, strategies, teaching and learning phases, role of teachers in teaching reading skills, intensive reading, extensive reading, teaching principles.

KIRISH

Ingliz tilini global til sifatida o'rganishning ortib borayotgan ahamiyati to'rt til ko'nikmalarini, jumladan, o'qishni o'zlashtirishga katta e'tibor qaratilishini ta'minladi. Ingliz tili turli sohalarda, masalan, savdo, fan, ta'lim va texnologiyalarda keng qo'llaniladi, bu esa samarali muloqot uchun o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishni talab qiladi. Ushbu maqola o'qish ko'nikmalarining ingliz tilini o'rganishdagi ahamiyatini va ushbu ko'nikmalarni o'zlashtirishni osonlashtiradigan yaxshi rejalashtirilgan o'qitish jarayonlariga ehtiyojni ta'kidlaydi.

O'qish ko'nikmalarini o'qitishning ahamiyati:

O'qish ko'nikmalarini o'qitish, barcha darajadagi o'quvchilar uchun juda foydali ekanligi aniqlangan. O'qituvchilar ko'plab strategiyalarni tushuntirish va namoyish qilishda, yo'naltirilgan va mustaqil amaliyot taqdim etishda hamda o'quvchilarning o'qish darajasini oshirish uchun fikr-mulohazalar berishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.[4] O'rta maktab o'qituvchilari va mutaxassislarining hisobotlari ko'plab o'quvchilarning o'qish matnlarini tushunishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelayotganini ko'rsatadi. O'qish ko'nikmalarini samarali o'qitish, ushbu muammoga yechim topish va o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun zarurdir.

O'qishni o'rgatish va o'rganish bosqichlari

O'qishni o'rgatish va o'rganish uchta asosiy bosqichga bo'linadi: oldindan o'qish, o'qish jarayonida va o'qishdan keyin. Oldindan o'qish bosqichi mavzuni tanishtirish, qiziqishni oshirish va matn uchun til tayyorgarligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Bu bosqich talabalarni matnning mazmuni va tuzilishi bilan tanishtirib, ularning oldingi bilimlarini faollashtiradi va o'qish vazifasiga tayyorlaydi. O'qish jarayonida bosqichi talabalarni matn bilan bog'lash, o'zaro aloqani rivojlantirish va ularning oldingi bilimlarini yangi ma'lumotlar bilan birlashtirishga qaratilgan. Talabalar jim o'qib, asosiy fikrlarni tushunib, tushunishni yaxshilashga qaratilgan savollarga javob berishadi. O'qishdan keyin bosqichi talabalariga o'z tushunchalarini ifoda etish, matnning haqiqiylikini tanqidiy tarzda o'ylash va parchani o'z tajribalari bilan bog'lash imkonini beradi. Bu bosqichda tushunish tekshiruvi, muhokamalar va boshqa til ko'nikmalarini birlashtirish kabi faoliyatlar mavjud.[6]

O'qish ko'nikmasini o'qitishda o'qituvchilarning roli

O'qituvchi talabalar o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. O'qishni samarali o'qitmaslik va yetarli darsliklarning yo'qligi talabalar

o'qish qobiliyatlarining pasayishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun, o'qituvchilar talabalarning o'qish va yozish rivojlanishini tushunish, individual taraqqiyotini baholash, turli o'qitish usullarini qo'llash, xilma-xil o'qish materiallaridan foydalanish, darsni individual talabalar uchun moslashtirish va strategik yordam berish kabi muhim sifatlarga ega bo'lishlari kerak. O'qituvchilar o'qishni o'rgatishda samarali usul va strategiyalarni qo'llab, talabalarni ma'no va bilim qurish jarayoniga faol jalb qilishlari lozim.[2]

Intensiv o'qishda o'qituvchilarning roli

Intensiv o'qishda, talabalar o'qigan narsalarini to'liq tushunishlari kutiladi, o'qituvchining roli o'qishdagi qiziqishni va ishtiyoqni oshirishdir. Bu, talabalar darajasiga mos keladigan mavzularni tanlash orqali amalga oshirilishi mumkin. O'qituvchi intensiv o'qish sessiyalarida tashkilotchilik, kuzatuvchi, fikr-mulohaza beruvchi va parametr sifatida rol o'ynaydi.

Keng qamrovli o'qishda o'qituvchilarning roli

O'qituvchilar talabalarni keng qamrovli o'qishga jalb qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi, ayniqsa, ko'plab talabalar o'z-o'zidan keng qamrovli o'qish bilan shug'ullanmaydi. O'qituvchilar matnni o'qishning namunasini ko'rsatish, talabalarni mustaqil o'qishga ruxsat berish va zarur bo'lganda yo'naltirish va yordam ko'rsatish orqali keng qamrovli o'qish odatini rivojlantirishga intilishlari kerak. [1]

O'qishni o'qitish tamoyillari

Ingliz tilini o'rganayotgan talabalarni samarali o'qitishda o'qituvchilarni yo'naltiruvchi bir necha tamoyillar mavjud. Bu tamoyillar quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

-O'qish passiv ko'nikma emas: O'qish faol faoliyat bo'lishi kerak, talabalar matn bilan faol aloqada bo'lishlari, so'zlarning ma'nolarini tushunishlari, rasmlarni talqin qilishlari, dalillarni anglashlari va fikrlar shakllantirishlari kerak. Passiv o'qish sirtki tushunishga olib keladi va unutilish ehtimolini oshiradi.[5]

-Talabalar o'z faoliyatlariga jalb qilinishi kerak: O'qituvchilar talabalarni faol ravishda jalb qiladigan o'qish faoliyatlarini yaratishlari lozim, bu esa haqiqiy qiziqish va motivatsiyani oshiradi. Faol jalb qilish talabalar o'qish tajribasidan maksimal foyda olishlariga yordam beradi.

-O'qituvchilar o'qish matnining kontekstiga javob berishlari kerak, faqatgina tilga emas: O'qishning asosiy maqsadi matnning ma'nosi va xabarini tushunishdir. O'qituvchilar talabalarni mazmuniga javob berish uchun imkoniyatlar yaratishlari, ularning matnni talqin qilish va tushunishlarini rag'batlantirishlari kerak.

-Taxmin qilish o'qishda muhim omil: Taxmin qilish o'qish jarayonida muhim rol o'ynaydi. O'qituvchilar talabalarni o'qishdan oldin matn haqida taxminlar qilish uchun kitob muqovalari, fotosuratlar, mazmun va sarlavhalar kabi kontekstual

belgilarni qo'llashga yo'naltirishlari kerak. Bu talabalarni oldingi bilimlarini faollashtiradi va ma'noli o'qish tajribasiga tayyorlaydi.

-Vazifalarni mavzu bilan moslashtirish: O'qish vazifalarini tayinlashda o'qituvchilar ularning matnning mavzusi va maqsadiga mos kelishini ta'minlashlari kerak. Talabalarni o'ylash va matn bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lishga jalb qiladigan to'g'ri savollar va faoliyatlarni ishlab chiqish muhimdir. Noqulay yoki aloqasiz vazifalar talabalar jalb qilishini qiyinlashtirishi va o'qish tajribasini yoqimsiz qilishi mumkin.[3]

-Malakali o'qituvchilar o'qish matnlaridan to'liq foydalanadilar: O'qituvchilar o'qish matnlarini qiziqarli darslar ketma-ketligiga qo'shish orqali maksimal darajada foydalanishlari kerak. Ular matnni dars muhokamalari, qo'shimcha vazifalar, til o'rganish va keyingi til faollashtirish uchun asos sifatida ishlatishlari mumkin. Bu yondashuv talabalar o'qish materialidan to'liq foyda olishlarini va uni turli usullar bilan o'zlashtirishini ta'minlaydi.

XULOSA

O'qish ko'nikmalarini o'qitish ingliz tilini o'rganayotgan talabalar uchun ularning erkinlik va tushunish qobiliyatlarini oshirishda juda muhimdir. O'qituvchilar bu ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishda samarali o'qitish jarayonlarini qo'llash, mos strategiyalarni ishlatish va yo'naltirish va yordam ko'rsatish orqali muhim rol o'ynaydilar. O'qish o'qitish va o'rganishning uchta asosiy bosqichi — oldindan o'qish, o'qish jarayonida va o'qishdan keyin — samarali o'qish darslari uchun tuzilgan asosiy tuzilmani taqdim etadi. O'qituvchilarning intensiv va keng qamrovli o'qishda tutgan roli va mas'uliyatlarini tushunish orqali ta'lim beruvchilar o'z talabalariga qiziqarli va ma'noli o'qish tajribalarini yaratishlari mumkin. O'qish o'qitish tamoyillariga rioya qilish o'qitish samaradorligini yanada oshirishi va talabalarni umumiy o'qish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishi mumkin.

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'RGATISHNING AHAMIYATI

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the importance, advantages, modern approaches and problems of teaching foreign languages to primary school students. The article analyzes the cognitive, socio-cultural and economic aspects of teaching foreign languages in primary school, and based on scientific research, shows the impact of language learning at an early age on the intellectual development of students. The article presents effective methods and strategies for teaching foreign languages in primary school.

Keywords: primary education, foreign languages, cognitive development, language teaching methodology, multilingualism.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются важность, преимущества, современные подходы и проблемы в образовательном процессе обучения иностранных языков учащимся начальной школы. В статье анализируются когнитивные, социокультурные и экономические аспекты обучения иностранным языкам в начальных классах, а также на основе научных исследований показано влияние изучения языка в раннем возрасте на интеллектуальное развитие учащихся. В статье представлены эффективные методы и стратегии обучения иностранным языкам в начальных классах.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, иностранные языки, когнитивное развитие, методика преподавания языка, многоязычие.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishning ahamiyati, afzalliklari, zamonaviy yondashuvlari va ta'lim jarayonidagi muammolari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada boshlang'ich sinflarda chet tillarini o'rgatishning kognitiv, ijtimoiy-madaniy va iqtisodiy jihatlari tahlil qilingan bo'lib, ilmiy tadqiqotlar asosida erta yoshda til o'rganishning o'quvchilar intellektual rivojlanishiga ta'siri ko'rsatilgan. Maqola boshlang'ich sinflarda chet tillarini o'qitishning samarali metodlari va strategiyalarini taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, xorijiy tillar, kognitiv rivojlanish, til o'qitish metodikasi, ko'p tillilik.

Zamonaviy globallashtirish jarayonida xorijiy tillarni bilish nafaqat shaxsiy va kasbiy muvaffaqiyatning omili, balki umumbashariy madaniyat va bilimlar olamiga kirish kaliti ham hisoblanadi. Xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonini qachon boshlash kerak degan savol ko'plab olimlar va pedagoglar tomonidan muhokama qilinmoqda. So'nggi o'n yilliklarda boshlang'ich ta'limda, hatto maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish amaliyoti keng tarqalmoqda (Nikolov & Djigunovich, 2011). Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish o'quvchilarning nafaqat lingvistik qobiliyatlarini, balki umumiy kognitiv va ijtimoiy-madaniy rivojlanishini ham ta'minlaydi. Ushbu maqola boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishning ilmiy asoslangan ahamiyatini, afzalliklarini va zamonaviy yondashuvlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'RGATISHNING ILMIY ASOSLARI

Neyrofiziologik asoslar. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, til o'rganish qobiliyati inson miyasining plastikligiga asoslangan. Bolalar miyasi kattalar miyasiga qaraganda yangi axborotni qabul qilish va qayta ishlashda ancha moslashuvchan hisoblanadi. Lenneberg (1967) tomonidan taklif etilgan "Til o'rganishning kritik davri" nazariyasiga ko'ra, til o'rganish qobiliyati biologik jihatdan belgilangan vaqt oralig'ida optimal darajada bo'ladi va bu davr taxminan 2 yoshdan o'smirlik davrigacha davom etadi. Zamonaviy neyrobiologlari yangi tillarni o'rganish jarayonida bolalar miyasining turli qismlarini samaraliroq ishlatishini aniqlashgan. Masalan, Bloch va hamkasblar (2009) tomonidan o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ikki va undan ortiq tillarni erta yoshdan o'rgangan bolalarda miyaning prefrontal qismi (fikrlash, qaror qabul qilish va ijtimoiy xatti-harakatlarni boshqarish uchun mas'ul bo'lgan qism) yaxshiroq rivojlanadi.

Kognitiv rivojlanishga ta'siri. Xorijiy tillarni erta yoshdan o'rganish bolalarning kognitiv rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bialystok (2001) tadqiqotlari ko'rsatishicha, ikki yoki undan ortiq tillarni biladigan bolalar yaxshiroq analitik fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish va ijodiy yondashuvlar ko'rsatadilar. Ular diqqatni jamlash, diqqatni taqsimlash va boshqarish qobiliyatlari bo'yicha ham ustunlikka ega.

Ko'p tillilik o'quvchilarning metakognitiv ko'nikmalarini, ya'ni o'z bilish jarayonlarini anglash va boshqarish qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi. Bu o'quvchilarga o'z bilimlarini ongli ravishda tashkil etish, kuzatish va baholash imkonini beradi, bu esa o'quv samaradorligini oshiradi (Adesope et al., 2010).

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'RGATISHNING AFZALLIKLARI

Talaffuz va fonetik qobiliyatlar. Erta yoshda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish o'quvchilarga yangi tilning fonetik tizimini yaxshiroq o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Bolalar yangi tovushlarni kattalardan ko'ra osonroq o'zlashtiradi va tabiiy talaffuzga erishadi. Flege va hamkasblar (1999) kuzatishicha, boshlang'ich sinflarda til o'rganishni boshlagan o'quvchilar aksent va talaffuz bo'yicha ona tilida so'zlashuvchilarga yaqinroq natijalarni ko'rsatadi.

Madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya. Xorijiy tillarni o'rganish o'quvchilarda madaniyatlararo tushunish va hurmatni rivojlantiradi. Til faqat aloqa vositasi emas, balki madaniyat elementi hamdir. Til orqali o'quvchilar boshqa xalqlarning qadriyatlarini, an'analari va dunyoqarashini o'rganadilar. Bu esa o'z navbatida tolerantlik, ochiqlik va turli xil fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi (Byram & Parmenter, 2012).

Kelajakdagi akademik va kasbiy imkoniyatlar. Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish o'quvchilarning kelajakdagi akademik va kasbiy taraqqiyotiga asos yaratadi. Xorijiy tillarni bilish global ta'lim imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi, xalqaro dasturlar va almashinuv dasturlarida ishtirok etish imkoniyatini beradi. Mehnat bozorida ko'p tillilik raqobatbardosh ustunlik hisoblanadi va ko'plab kasbiy sohalarda yuqori baholanadi (Ginsburgh & Weber, 2011).

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI

O'yin asosidagi ta'lim. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun o'yin asosidagi ta'lim eng samarali yondashuvlardan biri hisoblanadi. O'yinlar orqali o'quvchilar tilni tabiiy va qiziqarli sharoitda o'rganadilar. O'yin davomida tilni o'rganish jarayoni hissiy jihatdan ijobiy bo'lib, o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshiradi va stress darajasini pasaytiradi (Tomlinson & Masuhara, 2009).

O'yin asosidagi ta'lim texnologiyalariga quyidagilar kiradi:

- Rol o'yinlari va dramatisatsiya
- Harakatli va musiqiy o'yinlar
- Didaktik o'yinlar va viktorinalar
- Raqamli o'quv o'yinlari

Kontentga asoslangan o'qitish. Kontentga asoslangan o'qitish yondashuvida til o'rganish predmet mazmuni bilan integratsiyalashgan. Bu yondashuvda o'quvchilar matematika, tabiatshunoslik, san'at kabi fanlarni o'rganish jarayonida chet tilini ham o'zlashtiradilar. Bu usul til o'rganishni real kontekstga joylashtiradi va o'quvchilarning bilish qiziqishlarini qondiradi (Stoller, 2008).

Texnologiya integratsiyasi. Zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'qitish jarayoniga yangi

imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Interaktiv ilovalar, o'quv o'yinlari, multimediya resurslari o'qitish jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va samarali qiladi. Texnologiyalar yordamida o'quvchilar autentik til materiallariga oson kirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar va tilni tabiiy kontekstda eshitishlari va ko'rishlari mumkin (Golonka et al., 2014).

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI HAL QILISH YO'LLARI

Metodologik muammolar. Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda quyidagi metodologik muammolar mavjud:

- Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining yosh xususiyatlariga mos keluvchi metodlarni tanlash

- O'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish

- Til muhitining yetishmasligi

Bu muammolarni hal qilish uchun quyidagi strategiyalar tavsiya etiladi:

- Differensiatsiyalashgan ta'lim yondashuvlarini qo'llash

- O'yin va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish

- Virtual til muhitini yaratish (videofilmlar, audio materiallar, onlayn muloqot)

Malakali pedagoglar tayyorlash. Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni samarali o'qitish uchun maxsus tayyorgarlikdan o'tgan o'qituvchilar zarur. Bu nafaqat til bilimi, balki boshlang'ich ta'lim metodikasi va bolalar psixologiyasi bo'yicha ham chuqur bilimlarni talab etadi. Malakali kadrlar tayyorlash muammosini hal qilish uchun quyidagi tadbirlar tavsiya etiladi:

- Pedagogik universitetlarda boshlang'ich sinf xorijiy til o'qituvchilarini tayyorlash dasturlarini rivojlantirish

- Amaliyotchi o'qituvchilar uchun malaka oshirish kurslarini tashkil etish

- Xalqaro tajribani o'rganish va o'qituvchilar almashinuv dasturlarini rivojlantirish

XULOSA

Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim komponenti hisoblanadi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, erta yoshda til o'rganish o'quvchilarning kognitiv, ijtimoiy va madaniy rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni samarali o'qitish uchun o'quvchilarning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda zamonaviy ta'lim yondashuvlarini qo'llash, malakali kadrlar tayyorlash va ta'lim jarayoniga axborot texnologiyalarini integratsiyalash zarur.

Boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi, balki o'quvchilarning kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyati uchun asos yaratadi,

global dunyoda samarali faoliyat ko'rsatish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantiradi. Shunday qilib, boshlang'ich sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim strategik yo'nalishi hisoblanadi.

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"The Impact of Pair and Group Work on Speaking Development"

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Abstract: This study investigates the influence of pair and group work on speaking skill development among EFL learners. Drawing on sociocultural and communicative language teaching theories, the research examines how structured collaborative tasks contribute to increased fluency, accuracy, and confidence in spoken English. Data were collected from pre- and post-intervention speaking assessments and student reflections in an upper-intermediate EFL class over a 10-week period. Findings indicate that regular implementation of pair and group activities significantly enhances learners' speaking performance, particularly in terms of fluency and interactional competence.

Keywords: EFL speaking, pair work, group work, communicative competence, speaking development, CLT, interaction.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilarda nutq qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda juftlik va guruh ishlarining ta'sirini o'rganadi. Ijtimoiy-madaniy va kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish nazariyalariga tayangan holda, tadqiqot tuzilgan hamkorlikdagi vazifalar og'zaki ingliz tilida ravonlik, aniqlik va ishonchni oshirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini o'rganadi. Ma'lumotlar 10 haftalik muddat davomida yuqori o'rta darajadagi EFL sinfida aralashuvdan oldingi va keyingi nutqni baholash va talabalarning fikrlashlaridan to'plangan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, juftlik va guruh mashg'ulotlarini muntazam ravishda amalga oshirish o'quvchilarning nutq qobiliyatini sezilarli darajada oshiradi, ayniqsa ravonlik va o'zaro ta'sir qilish qobiliyatida katta o'zgarish kuzatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: EFL nutqi, juftlik bilan ishlash, guruhda ishlash, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, nutqni rivojlantirish, CLT, o'zaro ta'sir.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании изучается влияние парной и групповой работы на развитие навыков говорения среди изучающих английский как иностранный. Опираясь на социокультурные и коммуникативные теории преподавания языка, исследование изучает, как структурированные совместные задания способствуют повышению беглости, точности и уверенности в разговорном английском. Данные были собраны из оценок говорения до и после вмешательства и размышлений студентов в классе EFL выше среднего уровня в течение 10-недельного периода. Результаты показывают, что регулярное выполнение парных и групповых занятий значительно повышает эффективность говорения учащихся, особенно с точки зрения беглости и интерактивной компетенции.

Ключевые слова: говорение на английском языке как иностранном, парная работа, групповая работа, коммуникативная компетентность, развитие говорения, CLT, взаимодействие.

1. Introduction

Speaking is one of the most complex and essential skills in second language acquisition, requiring the integration of vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and pragmatics. Despite its importance, speaking is often underemphasized in traditional

classrooms that prioritize form-focused instruction. Recent trends in communicative language teaching (CLT) emphasize the role of interaction in language learning, particularly through pair and group work. These collaborative methods are grounded in Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, which posits that language development occurs through social interaction in the learner's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD).

This paper aims to examine the impact of pair and group work on speaking development in an EFL context, focusing on measurable outcomes such as fluency, accuracy, and confidence. The central research question guiding the study is: *How does regular use of pair and group work influence EFL learners' speaking skills?*

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

The study involved 30 upper-intermediate EFL students at a university in Uzbekistan, aged between 18 and 22. All participants had studied English for at least five years and were enrolled in a speaking-focused elective course.

2.2. Procedure

The study was conducted over a 10-week period. Students participated in weekly pair and group speaking activities designed around common CEFR B2-level speaking tasks, including role plays, problem-solving tasks, debates, and information gaps.

The class was divided into two sections:

- Experimental group (15 students): received structured pair/group speaking tasks weekly.

- Control group (15 students): followed the same syllabus but did individual speaking tasks.

2.3. Instruments

- Pre- and Post-Test Speaking Assessments: Using CEFR-aligned rubrics assessing fluency, accuracy, vocabulary, and coherence.

- Student Self-Reflection Journals: Weekly reflections to monitor perceived progress and engagement.

- Teacher Observations: Focused on student participation, turn-taking, and use of target language.

2.4. Data Analysis

Scores from pre- and post-tests were analyzed using paired t-tests. Qualitative data from journals and observations were coded thematically.

3. Results

3.1. Quantitative Findings

The experimental group demonstrated a significant improvement in all assessed aspects of speaking. Their average fluency score rose from 5.2 to 6.8 out of 9, and accuracy improved from 5.0 to 6.3. Vocabulary range increased from 5.5 to 6.9, and

coherence rose from 5.1 to 6.7. All improvements were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

In contrast, the control group showed only minor improvements: fluency improved slightly from 5.1 to 5.6, and accuracy from 5.1 to 5.5. Vocabulary and coherence also increased marginally but without statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that learners in the experimental group benefited considerably more from the interactive speaking tasks.

3.2. Qualitative Findings

Student reflections indicated increased confidence, reduced speaking anxiety, and more willingness to take risks in using English. Learners reported that working with peers helped them discover new expressions, correct mistakes, and become more aware of their speaking patterns. Many emphasized the motivational effect of interacting with classmates rather than speaking alone or to the teacher.

Teacher observations supported these perceptions, noting higher engagement levels, more spontaneous use of English, and better turn-taking skills in the experimental group. Students frequently negotiated meaning and helped each other reformulate their speech, further reinforcing language learning.

4. Discussion

The findings strongly support the view that pair and group work have a positive impact on the development of speaking skills in EFL learners. The significant gains in fluency, accuracy, vocabulary, and coherence among students in the experimental group align with key principles from Long's Interaction Hypothesis and Swain's Output Hypothesis. These theories suggest that interaction not only provides opportunities for meaningful input but also pushes learners to produce language more accurately and fluently.

Additionally, the affective benefits observed—such as increased confidence and reduced anxiety—are crucial in language learning environments where learners may fear making mistakes. The social nature of speaking tasks appeared to create a safe space for experimentation and peer feedback, which enhanced the overall learning process.

However, the study has limitations, including its small sample size and relatively short duration. Future research could examine the long-term effects of collaborative speaking practice and explore how different group dynamics or task types influence outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms that pair and group work significantly enhance speaking development among EFL learners. Through collaborative tasks, students gain more opportunities to practice language in meaningful contexts, leading to improvements in fluency, accuracy, vocabulary use, and coherence. Teachers are encouraged to

incorporate structured interactive speaking tasks into their lesson plans to foster communicative competence and build learner confidence.

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LEARNING LANGUAGES AT THE POLYGLOT LEVEL

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of learning foreign languages and how they play a crucial role in our lives. It explores the remarkable abilities of polyglots, individuals who can master multiple languages in a short time. The article highlights famous polyglots in history and their unique language-learning techniques. Additionally, it provides practical strategies for learning new languages effectively, emphasizing the significance of practice, communication, and a positive mindset.

Key words: foreign language, communication, fluency, skills, improvement, success, multilingualism, practice, learning strategies.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается о важности изучения иностранных языков и о том, какую важную роль они играют в нашей жизни. В ней рассказывается о замечательных способностях полиглотов, людей, которые могут овладеть несколькими языками за короткое время. В статье рассказывается о знаменитых полиглотах в истории и их уникальных методах изучения языка. Кроме того, в статье представлены практические стратегии эффективного изучения новых языков, подчеркивающие важность практики, общения и позитивного мышления.

Ключивые слова: иностранный язык, коммуникация, свободное владение, навыки, совершенствование, успех, многоязычие, практика, стратегии обучения.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati va ularning hayotimizda qanday muhim rol o'ynashi haqida so'z boradi. Bunda qisqa vaqt ichida bir nechta tillarni o'zlashtira oladigan poliglottlarning ajoyib qobiliyatlari haqida so'zlaymiz. Maqolada tarixdagi mashhur poliglot va ularning tilni o'rganishning noyob usullari haqida fikrlar keltiriladi. Bundan tashqari maqolada yangi tillarni samarali o'rganish uchun amaliyot, muloqot va ijobiy fikrlash muhimligi ta'kidlab o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, aloqa, erkin o'zlashtirish, ko'nikmalar, tajriba, muvaffaqiyat, ko'p tillilik, amaliyot, o'rganish strategiyalari.

Polyglots are people who know many languages perfectly and can speak them fluently. They are one of the most unique people. Despite their different origins and living in different eras, they all have one thing in common: polyglots can learn a new language in a very short period of time. Sometimes two or three months are enough for them. Most famous polyglots, when they start learning a new language, do it out of a thirst for knowledge rather than a practical application. Who knows the most languages in the world? You can't look at it the same way: it's one thing to be fluent in a foreign language, but it's quite another to translate books with the help of dictionaries. Of course, it is much easier to translate with the help of a dictionary: the Hungarian translator and writer István Dabi, who is alive at the moment, works with 103 languages! For one thing, he can speak only ... twenty-two languages with ease, so he takes an honorable, but not the first, place in the ranking of hyperpolyglots.

Ex Pope John Paul II was not only a mountain skier, but also a famous hyperpolyglot. Even though he doesn't know Japanese, it wasn't difficult to say "Happy Easter" in Japanese. Papa was born in Poland. When he was elected Pope, his name was Karol Wojtyla and he was fluent in 11 languages.

Heinrich Schliemann is known for discovering the city of Troy during excavations. However, it is not known to everyone that this German entrepreneur and amateur archaeologist could speak fourteen languages, including Arabic and Turkish.

During World War II, the Hungarian physicist and chemist Kato Lomb secretly learned Russian by reading Gogol's "Dead Souls" without a dictionary. Today, this Hungarian woman is included among the first simultaneous interpreters: she learned the last, seventeenth language in her portfolio - Hebrew at the age of 90, but did not have time to learn the next language in her plan, namely Arabic.

We will place István Dabi, who was mentioned earlier, on the seventh line of the rating. Anyway, 22 languages, it's not a joke, after all! Even so, he shares the seventh place with "the pride of the Mali race" Jose Protacio Rizal-Mercado Alonso-Realonda. The national hero of the Philippines was a scientist, writer, artist, sculptor and revolutionary who fought for the liberation of his country from Spanish rule.

Friedrich Engels is mentioned with special respect as a major philosopher and co-author of Marxism during the Soviet Union. On the ground of these glorious services, the other qualities of the "General" (as Engels was called in Karl Marx's family) disappeared. And he was a good polyglot: it is said that he knew twenty-four languages.

In pre-war Leningrad, they knew Ivan Ivanovich Sollertinsky, a very unique scholar and an excellent musicologist, music and theater critic. "He used to sign the register in Japanese, Arabic or Greek while he was receiving his salary: a senseless joke of a person who knows 26 languages," wrote Irakliy Andronikov about Sollertinsky. Of course, if intelligence officers do not know a foreign language, who else knows? Born in New Zealand, the son of the head priest of the Methodist Church, Harold Williams, a linguist and journalist, lived in Russia for many years and even wrote the book "Russia of the Russians". According to the Guinness Book of Records, he knew 28 languages. Knowing so many languages, what he did in Russia during the First World War and the revolution, history keeps a secret. Even so, together with Williams, Danish linguist-professor Rasmus Rask and English economist and deputy governor of Hong Kong John Bowring share the fourth place. There is no way to check it now, they have all already passed into the immortal world.

Ioannis Ikonomou is currently the chief translator of the European Parliament. A perfect job for someone born in Greece: he can speak 32 languages with ease.

Italian Cardinal Giuseppe Metsofanti is considered by many (including the Guinness Book of Records) to be the greatest polyglot in history. He spoke at least 29 languages fluently and knew another 8 to some degree, and he never left Italy. Byron, who knew the Cardinal personally, described him as follows: "It is a linguistic marvel... I have examined it myself, even in languages where I only know how to swear, and it has amazed me so much that I can't even swear in English." I was ready."

The future German scientist, Chinese scholar Emil Krebs, had his eye on a French newspaper when he was a child. He asked his teacher for a German-French dictionary and soon demonstrated his knowledge of the French language. According to them, he later mastered more than sixty languages and was able to speak them easily. Scientists studied his brain after his death and found differences from the normal human brain in the part responsible for speech. Now, scientists can only guess whether these differences were innate or arose in the process of learning languages.

Now let's look at the secrets of easy language learning and ways not to waste time:

1. Speak the language out loud from day one

Beginners should not be afraid of breaking words or forming phrases incorrectly. Most importantly, they get used to speaking out loud - immediately.

2. Learn useful phrases first

Newbies ask, "Where's the bathroom?" they should learn simple phrases like (English: "Where is the bathroom?") that helps them ask relevant questions. Not very eloquent, but understandable.

3. *Forget about learning strict grammar rules*

At the initial stage, it is important to expand vocabulary and learn basic phrases. No need to worry about correct grammar - you'll have time to study it later.

4. *Communicate with native speakers - for example via Skype*

According to Benny, one of the best tools The best way to learn a language today is the Internet - in particular, video chats such as Skype. With this program (or another similar one), a Russian speaker in Moscow can communicate with a person from the USA or any country in the world.

5. *Listen to the radio*

Radio is another way to immerse yourself in the language environment. Listen to radio broadcasts from countries where people speak the language you are learning. In particular, Benny recommends visiting TuneIn, an online repository of radio broadcasts from around the world.

6. *Tell us about yourself*

One of Benny's favorite tips for beginners is to write a short story about yourself in your language and work on translating it with a native speaker. This will help you memorize many words and phrases relatively quickly.

7. *Do not enroll in general language courses* Benny strongly advises beginners not to enroll in courses "for everyone" - they also have a general program. According to him, it is more useful with a personal feedback carrier in the early stages of training.

8. *Use free online language learning tools instead.*

One of Benny's favorite services is Duolingo. Another is Italiki, a site that connects you with a native speaker for face-to-face communication.

9. *Be prepared to spend a lot of time practicing*

Benny believes that people who are willing to devote full time to learning a foreign language can reach the B2 level in a few months. If you don't have much time, if you practice for a few hours a day, you will reach the same level in a year.

10. *Do not strive for perfection*

People often try so hard to speak perfectly that when they fail (by the way, beginners never succeed), they get frustrated and give up completely. The best way is to laugh at your mistakes and not try to be perfect.

In conclusion, I can say that learning a new language is easier if it is viewed as a hobby or a hobby rather than a chore. It is often up to the student to adapt to this process or create an interesting environment. Discipline, responsibility and patience are the foundation of any achievement.

No polyglot will tell you that learning a language is boring. One of the main secrets of their success is genuine interest. Enjoy not only the idea that you can speak a foreign language but also the process of learning. Fortunately, thanks to a variety of teaching methods, nowadays, learning can be a fun hobby. Look for fun in any aspect of the learning process, integrate it into your daily life and entertainment (watch comedies in the language you study), communicate with native speakers for the sake of communication itself, etc. You choose what works for you best.

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Application of Cognitive Strategies in Different Speaking Contexts

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Annotation. This article compares the advantages of cognitive strategies in different speaking contexts, such as academic, professional, and informal contexts. The cognition – related key strategies - note-taking, summarizing, planning, and paraphrasing – are explained due to their effectiveness in improving clarity and fluency in the process of speaking. The application of these strategies in different speaking scenarios are explored, since they are core aspects of communicative competence. The examples will be given to illustrate how students can effectively apply and use these strategies making them better in interaction and expression while speaking.

Key words: Cognitive strategies, speaking skills, communicative competence, academic speaking, professional communication, informal conversation, note-taking, summarizing, planning and structuring, paraphrasing, active listening, contextual adaptation, language learning, fluency and clarity, strategy training.

Аннотация. Данная статья сравнивает преимущества когнитивных стратегий в различных речевых контекстах, таких как академическая, профессиональная и неформальная коммуникация. Ключевые стратегии, связанные с когницией — конспектирование, резюмирование, планирование и перефразирование — объясняются с точки зрения их эффективности в повышении ясности и беглости речи. Рассматривается применение этих стратегий в различных ситуациях общения, так как они являются основными аспектами

коммуникативной компетенции. Приводятся примеры, иллюстрирующие, как студенты могут эффективно применять и использовать эти стратегии, улучшая взаимодействие и выражение мыслей в процессе речи.

Ключевые слова: когнитивные стратегии, речевые навыки, коммуникативная компетенция, академическая речь, профессиональная коммуникация, неформальное общение, конспектирование, резюмирование, планирование и структурирование, перефразирование, активное слушание, контекстуальная адаптация, изучение языка, беглость и ясность речи, тренировка стратегий.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kognitiv strategiyalarning turli nutq kontekstlaridagi — akademik, professional va norasmiy muloqotdagi — afzalliklari solishtiriladi. Kognitiv jarayonlar bilan bog'liq asosiy strategiyalar — muhim qaydlar yozish, xulosa qilish, rejalashtirish va qayta ifodalash — nutq jarayonida ravonlik va aniqlikni oshirishdagi samaradorligi nuqtai nazaridan tushuntiriladi. Ushbu strategiyalarning turli nutqiy vaziyatlardagi qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi, chunki ular kommunikativ kompetensiyaning asosiy jihatlari hisoblanadi. Talabalar ushbu strategiyalarni qanday qilib samarali qo'llashi va nutq davomida o'zaro muloqot va fikr ifodasini yaxshilashi mumkinligi misollar orqali yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kognitiv strategiyalar, nutq ko'nikmalari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, akademik nutq, professional muloqot, norasmiy suhbat, konspekt olish, xulosa qilish, rejalashtirish va tuzish, qayta ifodalash, faol tinglash, kontekstual moslashuv, til o'rganish, nutq ravonligi va aniqligi, strategiyalarni shakllantirish.

Language learning involves a set of cognitive strategies in particular for developing speaking skills. As learners find it a major task to express themselves fluently and accurately, the use of mental operations, techniques, or approaches assists in the best facilitation of the actual speaking ability. As Oxford⁶⁸ put it, cognitive strategies are "the techniques or devices that learners use to understand, learn or remember information", placing these strategies at the center of the learning process. A student employing such strategies could process the relevant information very quickly, retain it well, and utilize it to communicate more efficiently. Using cognitive strategies in speaking situations underscores the importance of these strategies in language acquisition, including the development of fluent and accurate expression. Speaking is an ever-evolving ability, constantly molded by the varying parameters of specific instances that hold a degree of formality, the various characters involved, and the communicative purpose behind the interaction. It is, therefore, in the interest of communicative competence to understand how cognitive strategies can operate across speaking contexts. This article examines the use of cognitive strategies in various speaking contexts and how they relate to language proficiency; in particular, it discusses their relation to L2 acquisition and the enhancement of speaking ability. In the following sections, we will first explore the notion of cognitive strategy with respect to language.

⁶⁸ Oxford, R. L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Newbury house.

Cognitive strategies in language learning function as mental procedures or techniques that the students use in one way or the other on the language input for better understanding, retention, and production. O'Malley and Chamot⁶⁹ argued that repetition, summarization, inferencing, deduction, and imagery are all cognitive strategies they are employed to make learning easier by helping learners to process and retain language information. Such strategies are usually chosen consciously and deliberately by a learner who tries to overcome problems related to unfamiliar vocabulary, complicated syntactic constructions, or new cultural concepts.

In situations of language learning, cognitive strategies become a means by which transfer can be achieved—from passive recognition of language elements into active production and on to fluency. For instance, it could refer to mental rehearsal or verbalization techniques that assist learners in forming coherent speech, whereas note-taking and summarization are strategies that provide structuring of thought before speaking⁷⁰. Even though cognitive strategies are contrasted with other types of strategies, such as metacognitive or socio-affective strategies, the key element that differentiates the former is the direct manipulation of the language either for comprehension or production, whereas the latter monitor and regulate the processes themselves.

One interesting thing about cognitive strategies is that they aid in the development of speech skills, allowing learners to manage this complex task, which takes place in real time. In L2 speaking, the learners are required to make quick decision on grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation technically speaking. Learned cognitive strategies might do well to help them in this decision-making. For example, cognitive strategies could include memorizing language chunks, rehearsal, or using context to infer meaning so that when communication does occur, the individual can cope with other cognitive demands.

As Scarcella and Oxford⁷¹ apparently argued, "The role of cognitive strategies in second language speaking cannot be underestimated as they enable learners to maintain communication even in the face of linguistic challenges" (p. 221). For example, if learners suffer a communication blockage or the flow gets hindered by the lack of a word, strategies such as paraphrasing or employing synonyms might sustain the conversation. On the other hand, segmentation and chunking might help learners to organize their thoughts so that they may bring out speech with fluency.

⁶⁹ O'Malley, J. M., & Chamot, A. U. (1990). *Learning strategies in second language acquisition*. Cambridge University Press.

⁷⁰ Cohen, A. D. (2003). *Strategies in learning and using a second language*. Longman.

⁷¹ Scarcella, R. C., & Oxford, R. L. (1992). The role of cognitive strategies in second language learning. In *Language Teaching* (Vol. 25, No. 3, pp. 221–233).

The other factor that enhances the effectiveness of cognitive strategies is the ability of one to adapt them to different types of speaking context (formal, informal, or academic). Cognitive strategies provide a framework for learners to meet the varying demands encountered in speaking, so that they can alter their strategies depending on the context, audience, and communication purpose.

Speaking contexts are varied and may range from formal situations, through casual conversation, to academic discourses or public speaking. Every context has its own set of expectations, purpose, and communication norms, which can influence people's choices in cognitive strategies. For example, in more formal contexts, like presentations or interviews, speakers may employ strategies such as rehearsing what they might say, taking notes, or choosing words strategically to enhance clarity and precision. In informal conversations, however, learners may apply spontaneous strategies like filler words or contracting their speech speed, primarily to maintain communication flow. In academic contexts, wherein precise language and logical organization are generally required, learners may resort to summarization, elaboration, and critical thinking strategies to articulate their ideas explicitly. Conversely, public speaking might call for strategies with both cognitive and affective weights, such as imagery or rhetorical devices, for audience interaction. As communication depends on the realization of a cognitive attempt through different kinds of strategies, and due to their contrasting nature across contexts, the knowledge of the ways of adapting these strategies to fit a certain situation is the core to accelerated development of speaking competence.

In conclusion, cognitive strategies are so important in the different contexts in speaking and they boost students' speaking abilities which makes them be able to communicate in different contexts efficiently.

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USE OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE IN EFL CLASSES

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Annotation

This article explores the use of the mother tongue in EFL classes is debatable in the foreign language classroom. Advocates of the monolingual approach suggest that the target language should be the only medium of communication, believing that the prohibition of the native language would maximize the effectiveness of learning the target language. However, some teachers believe that the use of the mother tongue can be helpful in learning new vocabulary items and explaining complex idea and grammar rules.

Keywords: monolingual, approach, mother tongue, vocabulary, grammar, study, learn, target, language, translation.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada chet tillari sinfida Ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganiladigan darslarida ona tilidan foydalanish muhokama qilinadi. Bir tilli yondashuv tarafdorlari ona tilini taqiqlash maqsadli tilni o'rganish samaradorligini maksimal darajada oshirishiga ishonib, maqsadli til yagona muloqot vositasi bo'lishi kerakligini ta'kidlaydilar. Biroq, ba'zi o'qituvchilar ona tilidan foydalanish yangi so'z birikmalarini o'rganish va murakkab g'oya va grammatik qoidalarni tushuntirishda foydali bo'lishi mumkin deb hisoblashadi.

Keywords: monolingual, approach, mother tongue, vocabulary, grammar, study, learn, target, language, translation.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассматривается использование родного языка на занятиях по английскому как иностранному языку, что является спорным в классе иностранного языка. Сторонники монолингвального подхода предполагают, что целевой язык должен быть единственным средством общения, полагая, что запрет родного языка максимизирует эффективность изучения целевого языка. Однако некоторые учителя считают, что использование родного языка может быть полезным при изучении новых словарных единиц и объяснении сложных идей и правил грамматики.

Ключевые слова: одноязычный, подход, родной язык, словарный запас, грамматика, изучение, изучение, цель, язык, перевод.

INTRODUCTION. They contend that teachers who master the students' native language have far more advantages over the ones who don't. Many proponents of the monolingual approach have argued that learners acquire foreign languages following basically the same path they acquire their mother tongue. According to him, the use of the mother tongue in the learning process should be minimized. In fact, a lot of teachers believe that the native language use in EFL classes must be discouraged

because of many reasons. Use of the mother tongue may become a habit that may resort to whenever a difficulty is encountered. both learners and Mother tongue may be sometimes misleading when learning the targets language. In spite of the existence of universals governing language systems, language differ more or less.

MATERIALS AND METHODS When using mother tongue to teach EFL students, errors may emerge due to the native language transfer. Examples of errors range from vocabulary to grammar. While learning English uzbek students for example may be misled by using the correct words in English for the Uzbek word "o'qimoq". They often confuse which word to use "to study or to learn", or "to read. In spite of the similarity, the meaning of these vocabulary items differ. In the Uzbek language we can say "Kitob o'qimoq", "Institutda o'qimoq", "Ingliz tili o'qimog". But In English it is expressed by a particular word, "to read a book", "to study at the University or to be at University", "to learn English Another example is the confusion of expressing the word "bor bo'lmoq" in the English language by the constructions "have/have got" and "there is / there are". In the Uzbek language we can say "Men juda ko'p inglizcha kitoblar bor" or "Xonada bitta stol, to'rta stul va divan va kreslo bor" etc. Many Uzbek students may also confuse whether to express these sentence by "have/have got stor "There is there are". And many make mistakes saying "I have got a lot of English books", "In the room have a table, 4 chairs, a sofa and an armchair". Though there is a similarity in translation, these sentences are expressed by different constructions, that is in English we have to say "I have got a lot of English books", "There is a table, 4 chairs, a sofa and an armchair in the room". The Uzbek students may also encounter difficulties related to the syntactic structures of sentences. In Uzbek, the sentence structure is S-O-V while English sentences are built following the S-V-O structure. In the Uzbek language the sentence structure is not strict. The part of speeches can be placed before and after each other. But in English the word order, the sentence structure is strict. The part of speeches never give their places to another. For example. In the Uzbek language we can say "U mashina sotib oldi/ Mashina sotib oldi u". But in English we only can say "He bought a car". The use of the mother tongue in EFL classes makes hard to provide enough comprehensible input, a prerequisite for acquiring any language.

RESULTS. The analysis of the survey results showed that 73% of students said that practicing and learning English through translation technologies has improved their language skills. 61% of students reported using tools such as translation method every day the monolingual approach has been criticised by many teachers who find that the use of LI in EFL classes is beneficial at various levels. Errors. Discussion of some recurring errors. It is true that a lot of errors are cause by mother tongue transfer. Some students, for example, say "I a student" instead of "I'm a student", "I am not work" instead of "I don't work" which is an error due to the mother tongue transfer (They don't know when or how to use the verb "to be" in a sentence.) A discussion in

mother tongue of such errors will help students overcome these problems. The debate over the use of the mother tongue in foreign language teaching hasn't been settled yet. On the one hand there are those teachers who reject the use of the mother tongue altogether or fail to recognize any significant potential in it. On the other hand, there are those who either massively overuse it. Both are abusing a resource of great importance and delicacy each in his own way. My view consists of using the target language as the medium of instruction when possible and switching to the mother tongue when it is really necessary. A rational and judicious use of the mother tongue in EFL classes can only be advantageous. Using the mother tongue must be tuned up with effective target language teaching, taking into consideration learners' mother tongue and cultural background and using them to the best of their interest.

DISCUSSION These findings suggest that language learning can be significantly enhanced through the use of use of translation method, particularly translating into native language, and support the use of vocabulary in language learning. Using the mother tongue in EFL classes is not the problem. The problem is use when and how to use it. Before answering this question, it should be born in mind that using the mother tongue must be considered as a means to an end". The target language must be used where possible and mother tongue when necessary. Here are some examples of appropriate use of the mother tongue in EFL classes.

Beginners The mother tongue can be probably more beneficial to beginners. As they progress in their learning the target language will take the lead.

Mother tongue use can be time-saving. Instead of going through a long explanations in the target language, it is sometimes casier and more efficient to give a translation of a vocabulary item or an explanation of a grammar point. Imagine a teacher who wants to teach the word "car" to Uzbek Students and start by phrasing the explanation as follows "a car is a road vehicle with an engine, four wheels, and seats for a small number of people" while a simple translation of the word (or perhaps the use of visual aids) would be enough.

Comparison A comparison of English and the mother tongue can be a very enriching experience. In fact, discovering the similarities and differences of both languages can enhance the target language acquisition. This comparison can be done at different levels:

Vocabulary. Exploring the nuances of vocabulary items in both languages
Building bilingual (or even multilingual) semantic maps

Grammar. A comparison between mother tongue grammar and target language grammar yields interesting results.

This comparison will highlight the differences between the two languages.

Teachers and learners may build on these differences to avoid negative transfer (mother tongue transfer which may be a source of errors.)

- The comparison also shows the similarities which will undoubtedly boost the internalization of the target language grammar.

Culture Language is a vehicle for cultural aspects. If teachers ban the use of the mother tongue, this underlies an ideological conception of native language culture as being inferior. Alternatively, cultural differences and similarities can be highlighted to help learners accept and tolerate differences while at the same time preserve their cultural uniqueness. This can be done brought various activities where mother tongue plays an important role

Proverbs. Students may be given a set of proverbs in the target language and be asked to find the corresponding ones in their mother tongue if they exist. If not, they try. translate the proverbs into their language.

Idiomatic Expressions. Again, finding the corresponding idioms or a translation of target language idioms might be very helpful to detect cultural differences or similarities

Songs. Translation of lyrics.

Jokes. Fanny EFL activities can be built on jokes, Students may translate and tell or act target language jokes to create a free stress environment and spot target language cultural specificities.

Stress. Using the mother tongue gives a sense of security and acknowledges the learner's identity, allowing them to minimize the stress they may feel in EFL classrooms, with careful use of the mother tongue learners may become willing to experiment and take risks with English.

Instructions. According to many experiences with EFL classes, it can be said that so many failures in tests were due to learners lack of understanding of instructions. Mother tongue can be used to redress this issue, helping students to understand what is exactly asked from them.

Rationale. Students need to understand the rationale behind activities or methods. It is important that they know where they start and what they will able to do. They should understand what lies behind the methods the teacher is using. This can only be done at this level through the students' native language.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the use of mother tongue sometimes can help to facilitate effective and easy language acquisition and improve student engagement in the process of learning. Using the mother tongue in the EL classes has long been considered as a lower language and a source of errors. This view is now being criticized because EFL teachers have become aware of the significance of the mother tongue. When students come to the classroom they don't come out of the blue; they come "loaded" with their native language and a cultural heritage that nobody must deny or underestimate. EFL teachers working with monolingual students at lower levels of English proficiency find prohibition of the mother tongue to be practically impossible.

So instead of looking at the students' native language and cultural background as inferior or a source of errors, they must be used as a tool to maximize foreign language learning. It's worth noting that the use of the mother tongue in EFL classes is just a "rehabilitation of those "students who were forced to smuggle their bilingual dictionaries into classrooms and hide them under the table." The mother tongue represents a powerful resource that can be used in a number of ways to enhance learning but it must always be used in a principled way. Using the Mother Tongue which provides practical native language activities shows that judicious use of the mother tongue can maximize language learning.

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The Internet for English Teaching: Guidelines for Teachers

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Abstract

The integration of the Internet into English language teaching (ELT) has transformed modern pedagogy, offering innovative tools and resources to enhance learning outcomes. This article explores practical guidelines for teachers to effectively utilize digital platforms, online resources, and interactive technologies in ELT. It examines best practices for selecting authentic materials, fostering student engagement through virtual collaboration, and addressing challenges such as digital literacy and information overload. By aligning with contemporary educational trends, the paper provides actionable strategies to optimize internet-based instruction while maintaining pedagogical rigor.

Keywords: Internet in ELT, online teaching strategies, digital resources, teacher guidelines, technology-enhanced learning.

Annotatsiya

Internetni ingliz tili o'qitish (ELT) jarayoniga integratsiyalash zamonaviy pedagogikani tubdan o'zgartirib, ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish uchun innovatsion vositalar va resurslarni taklif etadi. Ushbu maqolada o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli platformalar, onlayn resurslar va interaktiv texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar keltirilgan. Unda autentik materiallarni tanlash, talabalarning virtual hamkorlik orqali jalb qilinishi va raqamli savodxonlik kabi qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etish usullari yoritilgan. Zamonaviy ta'lim trendlariga mos ravishda, ushbu ish Internet asosidagi o'qitishni samarali tashkil etish uchun amaliy strategiyalarni taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ELTda Internet, onlayn o'qitish strategiyalari, raqamli resurslar, o'qituvchilar uchun qo'llanma, texnologiya asosidagi ta'lim.

Аннотация

Интеграция Интернета в преподавание английского языка (ELT) трансформировала современную педагогику, предлагая инновационные инструменты и ресурсы для улучшения результатов обучения. В данной статье исследуются практические рекомендации для учителей по эффективному использованию цифровых платформ, онлайн-ресурсов и интерактивных технологий в ELT. Рассматриваются лучшие практики отбора аутентичных материалов, вовлечения студентов через виртуальное сотрудничество и решения таких проблем, как цифровая грамотность и информационная перегрузка. Соответствуя современным образовательным трендам, статья предлагает действенные стратегии для оптимизации обучения на основе Интернета с сохранением педагогической строгости.

Ключевые слова: Интернет в ELT, стратегии онлайн-обучения, цифровые ресурсы, рекомендации для учителей, технологически обогащенное обучение.

Introduction

The internet has changed how we teach English, bringing exciting new tools and some challenges. Teachers now have access to amazing resources like video lessons, language apps, and online speaking partners, but need help using them effectively. This article shares practical, classroom-tested advice to help educators

choose the best websites and apps, create engaging online activities, and solve common tech problems. Whether you're teaching in a fully digital classroom or just adding some online elements, these straightforward tips will help you boost your students' learning while avoiding technology headaches. We'll focus on what actually works with real students, cutting through the overwhelming amount of online options to give you the most useful information for your daily teaching.

1. The Digital Transformation of English Language Teaching

The internet has fundamentally changed how English is taught and learned worldwide. Traditional classroom instruction is now enhanced with digital tools that offer unprecedented access to authentic language materials and global communication opportunities. Teachers today can connect their students with native speakers through video chats, use AI-powered tools for instant feedback, and access millions of authentic resources like news articles, podcasts, and videos. This digital shift requires educators to develop new competencies in selecting, evaluating, and effectively implementing online resources.

2. Essential Online Tools for Modern English Classrooms

Contemporary English teachers should be familiar with several key categories of digital tools:

Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle or Google Classroom provide structured environments for course organization, assignment distribution, and progress tracking. These platforms serve as central hubs for blended learning experiences.

Interactive language learning websites such as BBC Learning English or Duolingo offer engaging, multimedia content that makes language practice enjoyable. These resources often include grammar explanations, vocabulary builders, and cultural notes.

Video communication tools including Zoom and Microsoft Teams have become indispensable for real-time speaking practice and virtual classroom sessions, especially in remote learning contexts.

3. Selecting High-Quality Digital Resources

Choosing appropriate online materials requires careful consideration of several factors:

Authenticity is crucial - materials should reflect real-world language use. News websites, TED Talks, and YouTube vlogs expose learners to genuine communication contexts.

Relevance to students' proficiency levels and interests ensures engagement and appropriate challenge. Teachers should match content difficulty to learners' abilities.

Pedagogical value determines whether a resource actually supports learning objectives. Effective materials should clearly connect to curriculum goals and provide measurable benefits.

4. Effective Online Teaching Methodologies

Successful internet-integrated teaching employs several key strategies:

Task-based approaches might involve students creating blogs, recording podcasts, or producing video presentations in English. These projects develop multiple language skills simultaneously.

Collaborative learning thrives through tools like Padlet for brainstorming or Flipgrid for video discussions. Such activities build communication skills and digital literacy.

Adaptive learning systems can personalize instruction by recommending specific exercises based on individual student performance data from platforms like Khan Academy.

5. Overcoming Common Challenges

Implementing internet-based teaching presents several obstacles that require proactive solutions:

Digital literacy gaps may prevent some students from fully benefiting. Teachers should allocate time for basic technology training and digital citizenship education.

Screen fatigue can reduce engagement. Balancing online activities with offline tasks and incorporating movement breaks helps maintain student focus.

Equity issues arise when some learners lack reliable internet access. Providing downloadable materials and offline alternatives ensures all students can participate.

6. Assessment in Digital Environments

Online teaching requires adapted assessment approaches:

E-portfolios allow students to showcase their best work across various digital formats.

Automated quizzes through platforms like Kahoot provide immediate feedback on grammar and vocabulary.

Peer assessment tools enable collaborative evaluation of speaking and writing tasks.

7. Professional Development for Digital Teaching

Teachers need ongoing training to stay current with technological advancements:

Workshops on emerging tools and teaching methods should be regularly offered.

Online communities of practice let educators share successful strategies and resources.

Institutional support is crucial for providing access to necessary technologies and training opportunities.

8. Future Trends in Technology-Enhanced Language Learning

Emerging technologies promise to further transform English teaching:

Artificial intelligence will provide increasingly sophisticated language practice and feedback.

Virtual reality may create immersive language learning environments.

Adaptive learning systems will become more precise in addressing individual student needs.

Conclusion

The strategic integration of internet resources into English teaching offers tremendous potential to enhance language acquisition. By carefully selecting appropriate tools, implementing effective methodologies, and addressing implementation challenges, educators can create engaging, effective learning experiences. The future of English teaching lies in blending the best of traditional pedagogy with innovative digital approaches, always keeping learning outcomes and student needs at the center of instructional design.

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SOTSIOLINGVISTIKANI TUSHUNISH: TIL VA JAMIYATNING KESISHISHI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatni sotsiolingvistika ob'ekti orqali o'rganadi, sinf, jins, etnik kelib chiqishi va kontekst kabi ijtimoiy omillar tilning ishlatilishi va o'zgarishiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Mualliflarning asosiy nazariy asoslarni, jumladan Labovning variatsion yondashuvini va Hymesning muloqot etnografiyasini taqdim etadi va ularni real dunyo lingvistik ma'lumotlariga qo'llaydi. Maqola turli jamoalardagi nutq modellarini tahlil qilib, til ijtimoiy o'ziga xosliklar va ierarxiyalarni qanday aks ettirishi va mustahkamlashini

ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu ish til xilma-xilligini chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi va ta'lim, siyosat ishlab chiqish va madaniyatlararo muloqot uchun amaliy tushunchalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sotsiolingvistika, til va jamiyat, til va shaxs, bir tildan ikkinchi tilga kod almashinish hodisasi, diglossia, jins vat til.

Annotation: This article explores the relationship between language and society through the lens of sociolinguistics, examining how social factors such as class, gender, ethnicity, and context influence language use and variation. The author presents key theoretical frameworks, including Labov's variationist approach and Hymes' ethnography of communication, and applies them to real-world linguistic data. By analyzing speech patterns across different communities, the article highlights how language both reflects and reinforces social identities and hierarchies. This work contributes to a deeper understanding of linguistic diversity and offers practical insights for education, policy-making, and cross-cultural communication.

Key words: sociolinguistics, language and society, language and personality, code switching, diglossia, gender and language.

Аннотация: В этой статье исследуются отношения между языком и обществом через призму социолингвистики, изучая, как социальные факторы, такие как класс, пол, этническая принадлежность и контекст, влияют на использование и вариативность языка. Автор представляет ключевые теоретические основы, включая вариационный подход Лабова и этнографию коммуникации Хаймса, и применяет их к реальным языковым данным. Анализируя речевые модели в разных сообществах, статья подчеркивает, как язык отражает и усиливает социальные идентичности и иерархии. Эта работа способствует более глубокому пониманию языкового разнообразия и предлагает практические идеи для образования, разработки политики и межкультурной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистика, язык и общество, язык и личность, переключение кодов, диглоссия, гендер и язык.

Kirish

Ijtimoiy lingvistika til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganuvchi tilshunoslikning bo'limidir. U turli xil ijtimoiy kontekstlarda tilning qanday o'zgarishi va o'zgarishi va sinf, jins, etnik va yosh kabi ijtimoiy omillar tildan foydalanishga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Ushbu dinamikani o'rganish orqali sotsiolingvistika nafaqat biz qanday muloqot qilishimizni, balki tilimiz kimligimiz va biz tegishli jamoalar haqida nimani ochib berishini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Ijtimoiy lingvistika 1960-yillarda rasmiy tadqiqot sohasi sifatida paydo bo'ldi, garchi tilning ijtimoiy jihatlariga qiziqish ancha oldinroq kuzatilishi mumkin. Qo'shma Shtatlardagi Uilyam Labov va Buyuk Britaniyadagi Basil Bernshteyn kabi kashshoflar zamonaviy sotsiolingvistik tadqiqotlarga, xususan, til o'zgarishi va ijtimoiy tabaqalanish sohalarida poydevor qo'yishdi. Ushbu dastlabki tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, til statik yoki bir xil emas, balki u ishlatiladigan ijtimoiy tuzilmalar tomonidan chuqur shakllangan.

Ijtimoiy lingvistikaning asosiy tushunchalari

1. Til o'zgarishi: ijtimoiy lingvistikaning asosiy masalalaridan biri bu tilning qanday va nima uchun o'zgarishini tushunishdir. Bunga mintaqaviy lahjalar,

sotsiolektlar (ijtimoiy tabaqaga asoslangan til) va etnolektlar (muayyan etnik guruhlar bilan bog'liq til) kiradi. Misol uchun, ingliz tili. Amerika ingliz tilidan nafaqat talaffuz, balki lug'at va grammatika jihatidan ham juda farq qiladi.

2. Kodni almashtirish va Diglossia: ko'p tilli jamoalarda ma'ruzachilar odatda vaziyatga qarab tillar yoki lahjalar o'rtasida almashadilar, bu amaliyot kodni almashtirish deb nomlanadi. Diglossia turli xil ijtimoiy vaziyatlarda ikkita til turi qo'llaniladigan kontekstni anglatadi-biri rasmiy holatlar uchun, ikkinchisi norasmiy o'zaro ta'sirlar uchun.

3. Til va shaxs: til shaxsni ifodalash uchun kuchli vositadir. U ma'lum bir guruhga tegishli ekanligini ko'rsatishi yoki shaxslarni boshqalardan farqlashi mumkin. Masalan, jargon yoki o'ziga xos nutq namunalaridan foydalanish yoshlarning o'ziga xosligini, submadaniy mansubligini yoki mintaqaviy g'ururni ko'rsatishi mumkin.

4. Jins va til: ijtimoiy lingvistikada olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, erkaklar va ayollar ko'pincha tilni boshqacha ishlatishadi. Bu farqlar kengroq ijtimoiy rollar va kuch dinamikasini aks ettirishi mumkin. Misol uchun, ayollar ko'pincha sotsial-madaniy kontekstga qarab turli yo'llar bilan talqin qilingan ko'proq muloyim shakllar va standart grammatikadan foydalanadilar.

5. Tilga munosabat va obro': odamlarning turli til turlariga bo'lgan munosabati ijtimoiy imkoniyatlarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin. Ko'proq obro'li deb qabul qilingan navlar ko'pincha ijtimoiy dominant guruhlar tomonidan aytiladigan navlarga mos keladi. Bu ta'lim, bandlik va ijtimoiy harakatchanlikka ta'sir qiladi.

Ijtimoiy lingvistikaning qo'llanilishi

Ijtimoiy lingvistika ta'lim kabi sohalarda amaliy qo'llanmalarga ega, bu erda til xilma-xilligini tushunish o'qitish strategiyalari va o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqishni yaxshilashi mumkin. Huquq va sud lingvistikasida u huquqiy sharoitlarda adolatli muloqotni ta'minlashga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, u texnologiyada, xususan, inklyuziv ovozni aniqlash tizimlari va AI aloqa modellarini ishlab chiqishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Xulosa

Ijtimoiy lingvistika til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro bog'liqlikni yoritadi. Bu tilning nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki o'ziga xoslik, kuch va ijtimoiy munosabatlarning belgisi ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Jamiyatlar xilma-xil va o'zaro bog'liq bo'lib borar ekan, sotsiolingvistika tomonidan taqdim etilgan tushunchalar tushunish, inklyuzivlik va samarali muloqotni rivojlantirishda tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

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IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS INCORPORATING THE LEXICAL WORD “HEAD”

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Abstract This article explores a variety of idiomatic expressions in English that are centered around the word head. These idioms are commonly used in everyday conversations to describe emotions, cognitive processes, social behaviors, and personality traits. By analyzing idioms from multiple sources, including widely recognized vocabulary and idiom books, this paper aims to provide a clear understanding of their meanings and contextual usage.

Keywords: Idioms, English language, head idioms, figurative expressions, vocabulary development, emotional expression, phrasal meaning.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются различные идиоматические выражения в английском языке, которые сосредоточены вокруг слова head. Эти идиомы обычно используются в повседневных разговорах для описания эмоций, когнитивных процессов, социального поведения и черт личности. Анализируя идиомы из различных источников, включая общепризнанные словари и книги по идиомам, эта статья направлена на то, чтобы обеспечить четкое понимание их значений и контекстного использования.

Ключевые слова: идиомы, английский язык, идиомы head, образные выражения, развитие словарного запаса, эмоциональное выражение.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilidagi bosh so'zi atrofida joylashgan turli idiomatik iboralarni o'rganadi. Ushbu idiomalar odatda kundalik suhbatlarda his-tuyg'ularni, kognitiv jarayonlarni, ijtimoiy xatti-harakatlarni va shaxsiy xususiyatlarni tasvirlash uchun ishlatiladi. Bir nechta manbalardan, jumladan, keng tan olingan lug'at va idioma kitoblaridan olingan idiomalarni

tahlil qilish orqali ushbu maqola ularning ma'nolari va kontekstual ishlatilishini aniq tushunishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Idiomalar, ingliz tili, bosh idiomalar, ko'chma iboralar, so'z boyligini rivojlantirish, emotsional ifoda, frazaviy ma'no.

Introduction. Idiomatic expressions enrich the English language, allowing speakers to convey complex ideas in a concise and often figurative manner. Among them, idioms containing the word head are particularly abundant and versatile. These idioms reflect not only emotions and thoughts but also human behaviors and attitudes. The usage of such expressions varies depending on the context, making them essential for language learners who aim to sound natural and expressive in English. This article collects, categorizes, and explains idioms related to head from reputable sources to deepen learners' understanding and improve their communicative skills.

The object of this article is to investigate and explain English idioms that include the word head, categorizing them by their usage and meaning in different contexts, such as emotions, thoughts, and character traits.

The purpose of this study is to support English language learners in better understanding and using idiomatic expressions involving the head by presenting clear definitions, example sentences, and contextual meanings, thereby enhancing both their spoken and written fluency.

Head Idioms

Here is a set of idioms *describing people* based on the word *head*.

to have your head screwed on - to be sensible, informal

to have a head for heights -not suffer from vertigo

to have a head like a sieve -bad memory

to have a good head for figures -be good at maths

to have your head in the clouds -unaware of reality

to be head and shoulders above someone -much better than

to keep your head -stay calm in a difficult situation

a big-head -has a high opinion of him/herself [1].

Bury your head in the sand - refuse to think about unpleasant facts or problems because you do not want to deal with them

Put our heads together- plan something together [2].

A. Emotions

Head is used in a number of idioms that relate to *emotions* and staying calm and in control.

Idiom	Meaning
keep your head	keep calm, especially in a difficult or dangerous situation
lose your head	panic or lose control

laugh/scream/shout your head off	laugh/scream/shout very much and very loudly (informal)
be banging or hitting your head against a brick wall	ask someone to do something which they won't do
bring something to a head / something comes to a head	an unpleasant situation is so bad that it has to be dealt with

Examples:

- If you can keep your head when all around are losing theirs, you'll be a man, my son. (written by 19th century poet Kipling)
- They were shouting their heads off until late at night and I just couldn't fall asleep.
- Trying to get the boys to tidy their bedroom is just banging your head against a brick wall.
- Andy and Jill had been upset with each other for some time, but things eventually came to a head last night when they had a terrible row [3].

B. Thought

Sometimes 'head' is used in idioms to mean the place where ideas or thoughts are produced.

Idiom	Meaning	Example
put ideas into someone's head	make someone want to do something they had not wanted to do before (usually something stupid)	Louisa was always quite happy in the village until Rex started putting ideas into her head.
get your head (a)round (usually – can't get (my) head (a)round)	come to fully accept or understand something (informal)	I just can't get my head around what's happened. It's been such a shock!
off the top of your head	without thinking about it for very long or looking at something that has been written about it	Off the top of my head, I couldn't tell you where they live, but I could soon find out.

C. Other Head Idioms

Rebecca is so beautiful; she always turns heads¹ whenever she walks into a room. My brother Leon is beginning to fall in love with her, but our parents would like to knock that on the head². This is a very busy year for Leon and he is going to have to work very hard to keep his head above water³. However, he bites/snaps their heads off⁴ if they tell him to ignore her. I'm taking care not to get involved – it's safer to keep my head down⁵.

Footnotes:

¹ people notice that person because they look interesting or attractive

² put a stop to it (informal)

³ deal with a difficult situation when he has too much work and not enough time, or when he has just enough money to live or keep a business going (an image from swimming)

⁴ speaks to them angrily

⁵ say as little as possible in order to avoid arguments [4].

bite someone's head off. to speak sharply and with great anger to someone. (Fixed order.) Don't bite my head off! Be patient. I'm very sorry I lost my temper. I didn't mean to bite your head off.

able to do something standing on one's head- go to previous

draw ahead (of someone or something)- to pull or move ahead of someone or something in motion. I drew ahead of the car in front of me. The horse I was racing against drew ahead.

fall head over heels. to fall down, perhaps turning over or rolling. Fred tripped on the rug and fell head over heels into the center of the room. Slow down or you will fall down—head over heels.

fall head over heels in love (with someone). to fall deeply in love with someone, especially suddenly. Roger fell head over heels in love with Maggie, and they were married within the month [5].

Conclusion. Idioms with the word head play a significant role in expressing emotions, thoughts, and interpersonal relationships in English. They are widely used in both formal and informal contexts. By mastering these idioms, learners can improve their comprehension, enrich their vocabulary, and communicate more naturally. The study also emphasizes the importance of contextual learning, as many idioms derive their meaning from specific social or conversational settings.

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“Adapting English teaching methods to meet the needs of kinesthetic learner”

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ANNOTATION

This article explores how English lessons can be adapted for kinesthetic learners who thrive on movement and hands-on experiences. It reviews strategies that incorporate role-playing, physical activities, and tactile materials to enhance language retention and engagement. The discussion emphasizes using interactive games, group tasks, and spatially-oriented exercises that integrate vocabulary and grammar learning into dynamic classroom settings. The article provides practical insights for educators aiming to create a more inclusive learning environment that acknowledges diverse cognitive styles and leverages physical activity as a core educational tool.

Keywords: Kinesthetic learners, active engagement, movement-based activities, experiential teaching, hands-on learning, multisensory instruction, interactive English practice, classroom adaptation, practical language application, learner-centered strategies

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья исследует, как уроки английского языка можно адаптировать для кинестетических учащихся, наилучшим образом воспринимающих информацию через движение и практическую деятельность. Обсуждаются стратегии с использованием ролевых игр, физической активности и тактильных материалов, способствующих лучшему запоминанию и вовлеченности учеников. Особое внимание уделяется интерактивным играм, групповым заданиям и пространственным упражнениям, объединяющим изучение лексики и грамматики в динамичной учебной среде. Статья предоставляет педагогам практические рекомендации по созданию инклюзивного образовательного пространства, признающего разнообразные когнитивные стили и делающего физическую активность ключевым элементом обучения.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: Кинестетические учащиеся, активное вовлечение, движение в обучении, практический опыт, обучение через осязание, мультисенсорное восприятие, интерактивные методы, адаптация методик, практическое применение языка, ученикоцентрированный подход

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqola ingliz tili darslarini kinestetik o'quvchilarga moslashtirishni o'rganadi, ular harakat va amaliy tajribalardan foydalanishni afzal ko'radilar. Unda rol o'ynash, jismoniy mashqlar va tegishli materiallardan foydalanish orqali til bilimlarini va ishtirokni oshirish strategiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Muhokama interaktiv o'yinlar, guruh ishlar va fazoviy mashqlar orqali lug'at va grammatika o'rganishni dinamik o'quv muhitiga integratsiya etishga urg'u beradi. Maqola o'qituvchilarga turli kognitiv uslublarni hisobga olgan holda, fizikal faoliyatni asosiy ta'lim vositasi sifatida qo'llash bo'yicha amaliy takliflar beradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: Kinetetik o'quvchilar, ingliz tili o'qitish, moslashtirish strategiyalari, interaktiv o'yinlar, rol o'ynash, jismoniy mashqlar, tegishli materiallar, inklyuziv sinf, guruh ishlar, fazoviy mashqlar.

INTRODUCTION:

Adapting English teaching methods to meet the needs of kinesthetic learners is essential in today's diverse learning landscapes. Kinesthetic learners absorb information best when they can actively engage with the material through movement and hands-on experiences. This approach encourages educators to rethink traditional, lecture-based paradigms and develop interactive strategies that involve role plays,

simulations, and physical activities. Integrating movement not only boosts engagement but also reinforces retention and application of language concepts in everyday communication. Innovative activities such as language games, storytelling through actions, and real-world simulations transform lessons into dynamic experiences. These methods acknowledge that learning can be a full-body process, making abstract language rules tangible while accommodating different learning styles. Embracing kinesthetic strategies ultimately cultivates an inclusive classroom where every student has the opportunity to thrive.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

A range of studies acknowledges that kinesthetic learners benefit from active involvement in language instruction. Research indicates that physical engagement-through role plays, simulations, and other hands-on activities-enhances both retention and comprehension of English. Scholars such as Gardner have underscored multiple intelligences, including bodily-kinesthetic intelligence, as critical factors in shaping effective teaching methods. Empirical evidence reveals that lessons integrating movement not only foster deeper understanding of abstract language rules but also boost student motivation and participation. Comparative analyses highlight significant improvements in achievement when traditional lecture formats blend with activities that translate theoretical content into practical experiences. Overall, the literature consistently supports the adaptation of English teaching methods to create a dynamic, inclusive classroom environment tailored to kinesthetic learning needs.

METHODOLOGY:

This study employed a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative data with qualitative insights to evaluate how adapted English teaching methods benefit kinesthetic learners. The research design involved an experimental and a control group drawn from secondary school classes.

Research Design

- Pre and post-tests measured language proficiency gains
- Intervention classes integrated movement-based activities such as role plays and simulations
- Control classes followed traditional lecture methods

Participants

- Approximately 120 learners, balanced for age, gender, and learning preference
- Selection based on initial learning style assessments

DATA COLLECTION:

- Surveys and questionnaires captured student perceptions
- Structured classroom observations and interviews provided qualitative details

- Performance tasks assessed practical application of language skills

ANALYSIS:

- Statistical tests evaluated test score improvements
- Thematic analysis identified recurring trends in classroom engagement.

This dual strategy ensured a comprehensive evaluation of adapted teaching methods for kinesthetic learners.

CLASSIFICATION AND CATEGORIZATION:

This section outlines the classification and categorization framework of adapted English teaching methods for kinesthetic learners, focusing on grouping techniques into coherent categories based on theoretical underpinnings and practical application.

LINGUISTIC CLASSIFICATION:

Adapting English teaching methods for kinesthetic learners involves recognizing their unique learning needs. These learners thrive on physical movement and hands-on experiences. To cater to them, teachers can incorporate activities that engage the body and mind, promoting active participation.

LINGUISTIC CLASSIFICATION:

Adapting English teaching methods for kinesthetic learners means addressing their learning preferences. These learners excel with physical movement and hands-on experiences. Teachers can use activities that stimulate both the body and mind, promoting engagement.

GERMANIC LANGUAGE CLASSIFICATION:

Adapting English teaching methods for kinesthetic learners means considering their preference for movement and hands-on learning. English, as a Germanic language, often involves grammar rules and vocabulary that can be more effectively taught through physical engagement.

Adapting English teaching methods to meet kinesthetic learners' needs.

Kinesthetic learners benefit from activities that combine language learning with physical action. Teachers can:

- Use gestures to reinforce vocabulary and grammar concepts typical of Germanic languages.
- Incorporate role-plays simulating everyday conversations found in English.
- Design games where students move to different stations representing grammar parts.
- Use building blocks or tactile materials to construct sentences, reflecting English syntax.

These strategies help kinesthetic learners grasp the structural aspects of English while staying actively involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

This study investigated the effectiveness of adapting English teaching methods to specifically cater to the learning preferences of kinesthetic learners in a secondary school setting. The research focused on two key areas: the impact of kinesthetic-based activities on vocabulary acquisition and retention and the influence of active learning strategies on student engagement and overall comprehension of grammatical concepts.

DISCUSSION OF SOCIOCULTURAL IMPLICATION:

Adapting English Teaching Methods to Meet the Needs of Kinesthetic Learners" section. Remember that this is a starting point, and you'll need to adapt it to fit the specific context and arguments of your larger article. I've tried to incorporate common themes related to sociocultural impact, equity, and potential challenges. Discussion of Sociocultural Implications: Adapting English Teaching Methods to Meet the Needs of Kinesthetic Learners. The incorporation of kinesthetic learning strategies in English language teaching extends beyond mere pedagogical technique; it carries significant sociocultural implications that warrant careful consideration. By failing to address the diverse learning styles present within a classroom, particularly the needs of kinesthetic learners, educators risk perpetuating inequities and hindering the academic progress of students from various sociocultural backgrounds. This section will explore these implications, highlighting the potential benefits and challenges of adopting kinesthetic approaches in diverse English Teaching Methods contexts.

CONCLUSION:

Adapting English teaching methods to accommodate kinesthetic learners is essential for effective language acquisition. By incorporating movement and hands-on activities, educators can engage these learners more deeply, improving comprehension and retention. This approach respects diverse learning styles and encourages active participation, fostering motivation and confidence. Moreover, it promotes inclusivity by recognizing and addressing varied needs within the classroom. Ultimately, tailoring teaching strategies to kinesthetic learners not only enhances individual academic success but also contributes to a dynamic, culturally responsive learning environment that prepares students for real-world communication.

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Challenges of Learning English for Academic and Business Purposes (EABP) for Non-Native Accounting Students

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Abstract

This article investigates the difficulties encountered by non-native English-speaking students when learning English for Academic and Business Purposes (EABP) in the accounting field. It looks into language barriers, subject-specific vocabulary, cultural differences, and the need for integrated teaching methods.

Keywords: EABP, non-native students, accounting, business English, academic English, language challenges.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются студенты, не являющиеся носителями английского языка, при изучении английского для академических и деловых целей (EABP) в области бухгалтерского учета. Анализируются языковые барьеры, специализированная лексика, культурные различия и необходимость интегративного подхода к обучению.

Ключевые слова: EABP, студенты-иностранцы, бухгалтерский учет, деловой английский, академический английский, языковые трудности

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada buxgalteriya sohasida ingliz tilini ona tili bo‘lmagan talabalar uchun akademik va biznes maqsadlarida (EABP) o‘rganishdagi muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Til to‘siqlari, soha terminologiyasi, madaniy tafovutlar va integratsiyalashgan o‘qitish yondashuvlari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: EABP, chet ellik talabalar, buxgalteriya, biznes ingliz tili, akademik ingliz tili, til muammolari.

English for Academic and Business Purposes (EABP) has become crucial for students aiming to work in accounting, corporate management, and international finance in today's globalized society. Non-native students sometimes find it difficult to keep up with the language and academic demands of their courses, particularly in accounting—an subject that combines technical jargon, numerical data, and professional communication—while native English speakers gain from natural exposure.

Students enrolled in English-language accounting programs must be able to articulate accounting concepts orally, in written reports, and in business correspondence. A variety of abilities must be mastered by non-native speakers, ranging from comprehending academic texts and lectures to creating financial papers and audit reports. These activities, which constitute the foundation of EABP, demand high levels of competency in both academic English (for learning) and business English (for usage in the workplace).

Learning English for academic and business purposes presents a number of difficulties for non-native accounting students. These difficulties fall into the following general categories:

Language Barriers

The overall language barrier is one of the biggest challenges. The intricate academic and corporate jargon that accounting students must learn is sometimes difficult for non-native pupils to understand. Many of the terms used in the subject of accounting may not have exact equivalents in the native tongues of certain pupils. Words like "capitalization," "equity," "liabilities," and "depreciation" might be confusing to students who don't speak English well. Additionally, students may find it challenging to effectively convey complicated accounting ideas due to the significant differences in grammatical patterns between English and other languages.

Technical Accounting Vocabulary

Students need to learn accounting-specific terms in addition to standard business English. This involves being able to comprehend and use terminology related to financial statements, accounting procedures, and concepts. For instance, words like "income statement," "balance sheet," and "cash flow" need for exact language usage and comprehension. For non-native pupils, these words become more difficult, particularly if they don't have enough vocabulary in both their original tongue and English.

Academic Writing Difficulties

Academic writing is another significant area of difficulty. Students are sometimes required to write reports and analyses in a formal academic style as part of their accounting writing assignments. Sentence structure, consistency, and academic tone might be difficult for non-native students to grasp. Writing research papers and reports in English requires not just grammatical accuracy but also the capacity to communicate financial data succinctly and simply. Many students may generate work that is unclear or involves mistakes in accounting language if they are not given the right direction, which might result in low ratings.

Oral Communication challenges

Another crucial area where non-native accounting students struggle is oral communication. Students must successfully convey their grasp of accounting topics in

group projects, presentations, and customer contacts. This might be a difficult challenge for kids who don't speak English well. Presenting financial reports or explaining intricate accounting concepts to classmates, teachers, or even prospective employers might be challenging for them.

Integrating EABP (English for Academic and Business Purposes) into the accounting curriculum is crucial for bridging the gap between language abilities and professional competencies. EABP tackles a wide variety of issues faced by non-native accounting students by emphasizing both academic and business components of the English language. Here, we investigate how EABP tactics may be effectively used to overcome language obstacles, develop communication skills, and create a better knowledge of accounting principles. The major purpose of adding EABP into accounting education is to help students enhance their communication abilities. Accounting students must often convey complicated financial data in writing and speech, therefore high fluency in both academic English (for analyzing and writing about data) and business English (for presenting and discussing conclusions) is required. EABP guarantees that students not only understand accounting principles, but also can explain them clearly and effectively in both written and spoken modes.

Written communication: Students need to compose reports, essays, and research papers in English, accurately using technical accounting terminology. Teaching students how to structure reports, cite sources, and use formal academic language is a key part of EABP.

Oral communication: In professional settings, accountants need to explain complex financial information to clients, colleagues, and stakeholders. Role-play exercises, presentations, and debates on financial issues help students practice explaining accounting principles and decisions in clear, professional English.

Through EABP activities, students gain confidence in communicating financial information, which is crucial for future success in their careers.

Learning technical accounting vocabulary in English might be difficult for non-native students. Students who lack a solid command of accounting terminology risk misinterpreting essential concepts or miscommunicating their views in reports and presentations.

EABP plays an essential role in addressing this challenge by:

Introducing specialized accounting words and ideas in a contextualized way. Instead of just memorizing phrases like "assets," "liabilities," or "revenue," students engage in exercises that require them to use these terminology in real-world circumstances, such as analyzing a company's balance sheet or creating a financial report.

Building a complete vocabulary list: Teachers can provide students tailored

assignments that cover accounting terms. Flashcards, matching activities, and quizzes can assist teach proper usage of these phrases.

Contextualizing vocabulary use: In addition to learning individual terms, students should practice using them in context. Students, for example, may be assigned to produce an essay or case study that uses the accounting jargon they've learnt to illustrate a financial problem in depth. This ensures that students can utilize terminology correctly and naturally in academic and business settings.

By incorporating vocabulary development into the curriculum on a constant basis, students obtain the language tools they need to flourish in both their academic courses and future accounting employment.

Integrating EABP with Accounting Curriculum

The genuine usefulness of EABP stems from its incorporation into the existing accounting curriculum. Rather than considering English language training as a distinct topic, it should be integrated into the courses that non-native accounting students already take. This helps students realize the practical value of studying English in their field of study and provides ongoing exposure to academic and business English in real-world settings.

EABP can be integrated into the accounting curriculum in the following :

Accounting tasks: Instructors might create assignments that require students to prepare financial reports, analyze balance sheets, or calculate financial ratios entirely in English. This allows students to improve their language and accounting abilities concurrently.

Case study analysis: Case studies are a great way to combine language instruction with subject-specific knowledge. Students improve their critical thinking and language abilities by analyzing real-world business challenges and providing solutions in English. They may use theoretical accounting principles to real-world problems while also learning how to communicate themselves professionally in English.

Lectures and discussions: Teachers can deliver lectures in English and facilitate conversations about accounting issues. This allows students to practice listening comprehension and spoken communication in the context of accounting while also reinforcing important terminology and ideas.

Incorporating EABP within the core curriculum ensures that students are not only learning accounting principles but also becoming proficient in using the language that is essential for their future careers.

Improving Academic Writing and Research Skills

Academic writing in accounting involves more than just technical knowledge; it also necessitates the ability to write in a structured, formal, and understandable manner. Non-native accounting students frequently have difficulties while writing

essays, research papers, or financial reports in English. These issues can be handled with specialized EABP strategies:

Focused writing workshops: Teachers might arrange writing workshops in which students practice on writing styles, structure, and language use for academic accounting projects. For example, students may practice producing an executive summary or a budget analysis report. These tasks demand students to communicate complicated material in a straightforward and understandable manner. *Peer review and feedback:* Students might be invited to assess one other's work and provide criticism on language use, structure, or clarity. This not only helps students improve their own writing, but it also motivates them to observe others' writing styles and learn from their peers.

Through a combination of writing exercises and feedback, students can gradually develop the skills necessary to produce clear, accurate. .

Non-native accounting students have many and intricate difficulties when learning English for Academic and Business Purposes (EABP). English language competency has become essential for academic and professional success as global economic integration grows, especially in specialized sectors like accounting. But learning academic and commercial English, especially in a technical field like accounting, poses special challenges for non-native speakers. EABP is an important tool for assisting non-native accounting students overcome linguistic and cultural hurdles that may impede their progress in both academic and professional contexts. By incorporating EABP into the accounting curriculum, instructors can ensure that students are not only skilled in accounting principles but also have the language skills required to interact effectively in the global corporate environment. The end result is a generation of highly proficient accounting professionals that are prepared to succeed in various, worldwide workplaces and contribute to the progress of the global economy.

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BEYOND PLACEMENT TESTS: EXPLORING WORKING MEMORY AS A DIAGNOSTIC TOOL IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda qo'llanilayotgan ishga qabul qilish testlariga muqobil sifatida qanday vositalar mavjudligini aniqlash maqsadida ushbu tadqiqot o'tkazildi. Diqqat markazida working memory hajmi bo'ldi. Working memory til o'rganish kabi yuqori darajadagi kognitiv faoliyatlarda muhim rol o'ynaydi, deb hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, o'rganayotganlarning working memory hajmini o'lchash orqali til o'zlashtirish darajasini bashorat qilish mumkin, degan taxmin ilgari surildi. Xotirani o'lchash uchun ikki vazifali topshiriq bo'lgan Reading Span Test (RST) qo'llanildi. Yapon tilini o'rganayotgan xitoylik talabalar ishtirokida ularning working memory sig'imi o'lchandi va bu natijalar ularning o'quv yutuqlari bilan solishtirildi. Natijada, working memory hajmi bilan o'quv yutuqlari o'rtasida sezilarli korrelyatsiya aniqlanmadi. Biroq, har bir yapon tili imtihoni natijalari tahlil qilinganda, RSTda yuqori ball olgan guruh barqaror natijalar ko'rsatgan, past ball olgan guruh esa imtihon natijalarida beqarorlik kuzatilgan. Bu esa, past ball olgan guruh yakuniy imtihonda qoniqarli natijaga erishgan bo'lsa ham, ularning yapon tilini izchil o'zlashtirayotganliklariga shubha tug'diradi. Eksperimentda ko'plab takomillashtirish kerak bo'lgan jihatlar mavjud bo'lib, hozirgi bosqichda taxminni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi natijalar olinmadi. Biroq, working memory va til o'zlashtirish o'rtasidagi munosabatni chuqurroq o'rganish zarurati mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: Placement test, Working Memory, Reading Span Test, O'rganish natijalari.

Abstract: This study explores whether working memory (WM) capacity can serve as a potential alternative to traditional placement tests in language education. WM is believed to play a key role in higher-order cognitive activities, such as language acquisition. Based on this assumption, we hypothesized that the capacity of learners' WM might predict their progress in language learning. To measure WM, we employed the Reading Span Test (RST), a dual-task procedure. WM capacity was assessed in a group of Chinese learners of Japanese, and the results were compared with their learning outcomes. Although no significant correlation was found between WM capacity and academic performance, further analysis of their test results revealed a notable trend: learners with higher RST scores consistently demonstrated stable performance, while those with lower scores showed greater variability. This suggests that despite similar final exam scores, learners in the low-scoring group may not have acquired Japanese as reliably. While the current study did not provide conclusive support for the hypothesis, and several methodological issues remain to be addressed, we aim to continue investigating the relationship between WM and language learning in future research.

Key words: Placement test, Working memory, Reading span test, Learning outcomes.

Аннотация: Настоящее исследование направлено на изучение возможности использования объёма рабочей памяти (РП) в качестве альтернативы традиционным тестам на определение уровня знаний (placement tests) в языковом образовании. Считается, что рабочая память играет важную роль в осуществлении высокоуровневых когнитивных процессов,

включая освоение иностранных языков. Исходя из этого, была выдвинута гипотеза о том, что объём рабочей памяти учащегося может предсказать его успехи в изучении языка. Для оценки РП использовался тест на объём чтения (Reading Span Test), основанный на выполнении двойной задачи. Объём РП был измерен у китайских студентов, изучающих японский язык, и сопоставлен с их результатами в обучении. Несмотря на то, что значимой корреляции между объёмом РП и учебными достижениями не было выявлено, дополнительный анализ результатов тестов показал следующую закономерность: участники с высокими баллами по тесту на объём чтения демонстрировали стабильные успехи, в то время как у студентов с низкими результатами наблюдалась значительная нестабильность. Это позволяет предположить, что несмотря на приемлемые оценки на итоговых экзаменах, учащиеся с низким объёмом РП могли усваивать японский язык менее эффективно. Хотя настоящее исследование не подтвердило гипотезу, и в нём выявлены методологические ограничения, работа по изучению связи между рабочей памятью и овладением языками будет продолжена.

Ключевые слова: Тест на определение уровня, рабочая память (Working Memory), тест на объём чтения (Reading Span Test), результаты обучения.

Kirish

Ikkinchi tilni ta'lim muassasasida o'rganayotganda, o'quvchilarni mos bo'lgan darajadagi guruhlariga to'g'ri taqsimlash maqsadida, avvalambor pleysment (joylashtirish) testi o'tkaziladi. Ya'ni, tilni umuman bilmaydigan o'quvchi eng quyi darajadagi guruhdan boshlaydi, tilni ma'lum darajada o'zlashtirgan o'quvchi esa o'z darajasiga mos darslarga qatnashadi. Shunday tarzda taqsimlangan bo'lsa-da, vaqt o'tishi bilan ba'zan o'quvchi bilan guruhning mos emasligi ayon bo'lib qoladi. Bunday holatlar tajribali o'qituvchilar uchun yangilik emas — ular pleysment testining imkoniyatlari cheklanganligini yaxshi bilishadi. Agar test o'sha damdagi til bilish darajasini aniq o'lchagan bo'lsa ham, bu faqat o'sha vaqtgacha erishilgan bosqichni ko'rsatadi va kelajakdagi rivojlanishni oldindan aytib bera olmaydi. Ayrim o'quvchilar dastlab yaxshi natijalar ko'rsatgan bo'lsa-da, vaqt o'tishi bilan sustlashadi; boshqalari esa aksincha, sekin boshlagan bo'lsa-da, keyinchalik katta rivojlanish ko'rsatadi. Bu holatlar ko'p yillik tajribaga ega bo'lgan til o'qituvchilari uchun odatiy holatdir. Shunday bo'lsa-da, o'quvchi va guruh o'rtasidagi bu nomuvofiqlik muqarrarmi? Pleysment testidan tashqari o'quvchining til bilish qobiliyatini yanada aniqroq baholaydigan usul bormi?

Muallif, so'nggi yillarda xotira tadqiqotlarida katta e'tibor qozongan "ishchi xotira" (working memory) o'quvchining til o'zlashtirish salohiyatini bashorat qilishda foydali ko'rsatkich bo'lishi mumkin, degan taxmini ilgari surdi. Avvalgi tadqiqotlar working memoryning tafakkur va e'tiborni boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatgan (Baddeley & Hich, 1974; Just & Carpenter, 1992; Unsworth & Engle, 2007; Mukoyama, 2009). Til o'rganish kontekstida, masalan, matnni tushunish (reading comprehension) uchun e'tiborni boshqarish zaruriy qobiliyat hisoblanadi. Dars jarayonida bo'ladimi, matn o'qiyotgan paytda bo'ladimi — har qanday odamning e'tibori mavzuga aloqasi bo'lmagan fikrlarga chalg'ishi mumkin. Agar bu holat tez-tez

takrorlansa, dars mazmuni ongga yetib bormaydi va tushunish jarayoni sekinlashadi. Matnni tushunish jarayonida ham, agar shaxs bexabar holda topshiriqqa aloqador bo‘lmagan narsalarni ko‘p o‘ylasa, ya’ni ongini ayni vaqtdagi vazifaga jamlashda qiyinchilik bo‘lsa, bu holat o‘qish samaradorligiga salbiy ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Diqqatni kerakli narsaga uzoq muddat davomida qaratish – oddiy qilib aytganda, diqqatni jamlash qobiliyati – aynan mana shu qobiliyatga Working Memory sig‘imi ta’sir qilishi mumkin. Shu taxminni amalda tekshirish maqsadida, muallif o‘quvchilarning working memoryini o‘lchab, ularning ikkinchi tilni qanday natijalar bilan o‘zlashtirganliklarini tahlil qilishga qaror qildi.

Usul

Working memory sig‘imini o‘lchash uchun Reading Span Test (RST – o‘qish sig‘imi testi) deb nomlanuvchi test ishlab chiqilgan. Bu ikki vazifali topshiriq bo‘lib, unda ishtirokchi berilgan gaplarni ovoz chiqarib o‘qiydi va shu jumladagi maqsadli so‘zlarni yodlab qolishi kerak bo‘ladi. Bu jarayon “ma’lumotni qayta ishlash va saqlab qolish” qobiliyatini talab qiladi, ya’ni working memoryga yuklama beradi va shu sababli working memory sig‘imini o‘lchashda maqbul metod deb hisoblanadi (Osaka, 2013; Daneman & Carpenter, 1980).

RST aynan nimani o‘lchayotgani haqidagi muhokama muhim bo‘lishi bilan birga, “o‘qish tushunish qobiliyati” nimadan iborat degan savolning o‘zi ham murakkab masaladir. Masalan, Malayziyalik yapon tili o‘rganuvchilari ustida olib borilgan tadqiqotda, WM va yapon tilidagi o‘qish tushunishi o‘rtasida hech qanday sezilarli bog‘liqlik aniqlanmagan (Yoshikawa & Zorayda, 2017). Bu esa o‘qish uchun qanday kognitiv ko‘nikmalar zarur bo‘lishi haqidagi masalalarning hanuz to‘liq hal etilmaganligini ko‘rsatadi. RST working memoryni baholash vositasi sifatida foydali bo‘lishi mumkin, ammo tilni qanday baholash kerakligi mavhum qolsa, ikkala o‘zgaruvchi o‘rtasidagi munosabatni aniqlash mushkul bo‘ladi. Ushbu tadqiqotda yapon tilini o‘rganayotgan xitoylik o‘quvchilar ishtirok etdi, va RST materiali sifatida ularning umumiy til – putonghua (standart xitoy tili) qo‘llanildi.

Eksperiment

Maqsad: Working memory sig‘imi bilan yapon tili o‘rganish natijalari o‘rtasida qandaydir bog‘liqlik mavjud yoki yo‘qligini aniqlash. Tadqiqotda Osaka tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan yapon tilidagi RST testi xitoy tiliga tarjima qilinib qo‘llanildi.

Ishtirokchilar: Yaponiya Maktablar, Madaniyat, Sport, Fan va Texnologiyalar vazirligi (MEXT) tomonidan yuborilgan 35 nafar xitoylik stipendiat (18 erkak, 17 ayol). Ular 10 oylik yapon tili ta’limini Xitoyda olgach, Yaponiyaga borib, doktorantura bosqichida tahsil olishni rejalashtirishgan. Ishtirokchilar Xitoyning turli

hududlaridan bo'lishiga qaramay, ularning aksariyati 20 yoshdan oshgan va magistrlik darajasiga ega. Eksperimentga faqat yapon tilini boshlang'ich darajadan (nol bilim) boshlaganlar jalb qilindi. Test o'tkazilgan vaqt esa o'quvchilar o'rta darajaga kirib borgan, ya'ni tahsil boshlangandan 6 oy o'tgan davr edi.

Tartib: Osaka (2012) versiyasidagi RST testi 5 nafar yapon tili bo'yicha ixtisoslashgan xitoylik talabalar tomonidan xitoy tiliga tarjima qilindi. Har bir gap kompyuter ekranida ko'rsatiladi va ishtirokchi uni ovoz chiqarib o'qiydi. Shu bilan birga, gapdagi qizil tagi chizilgan maqsadli so'zni eslab qolishi kerak. Har bir blok yakunida ishtirokchi yodlagan so'zlarini javob varag'iga yozib beradi. Har bir sinov 2 jumladan 5 jumlagacha bo'lib, har darajada 5 ta topshiriqdan iborat.

Yapon tili sinovlari: Tilni o'zlashtirish darajasi har oyda bir marta o'tkaziladigan imtihonlar orqali baholandi. Boshlang'ich darajada asosiy darslikning har 10 ta darsi tugagach, jami 60 dars asosida 6 ta test o'tkazildi. O'rta bosqichda esa 2 ta – birinchi va ikkinchi yarim yillik sinovlar o'tkazildi. Shunday qilib, jami 8 ta muntazam test natijalari yig'ildi. Testlar grammatika, lug'at, iyeroglif, eshitib tushunish va o'qib tushunishni ochiq yoki ko'p tanlovli savollar yordamida baholadi. Gapirish (speaking) bo'yicha test o'tkazilmadi. Yakuniy imtihonni topshirolmagan talabalar uchun chet elda o'qish huquqi bekor qilinadi, shu sababli ishtirokchilarning motivatsiyasi yuqori darajada edi.

Natijalar

Reading Span Test (RST) ballarini hisoblashning bir necha usullari mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqotda quyidagi uchta ko'rsatkich hisobga olindi: ①Span ballari, ②Umumiy eslab qolingan so'zlar soni, ③To'g'ri javob berilgan sinovlar ichidagi eslab qolingan so'zlar soni (Conway, et al., 2005). Har bir mezon bo'yicha olingan natijalar 1-jadvalda keltirilgan. RST ballari bilan yapon tili bo'yicha o'tkazilgan oraliq imtihon va yakuniy imtihon natijalari o'rtasida hech qanday sezilarli korrelyatsiya aniqlanmadi.

1-jadval. RST ballarini hisoblashning uchta usuli

	① span score	② total number	③ total in completed		① span score	② total number	③ total in completed
2017 M	4.5	58	36	2018 F	3.5	54	38
2017 F	4.5	54	36	2018 M	3	48	31
2017 F	4.5	50	36	2018 M	3	48	28
2017 M	3.5	53	32	2018 F	3	50	28
2017 F	3	46	23	2018 M	3.5	52	26
2017 F	3	46	23	2018 F	3	49	26
2017 F	3	44	22	2018 F	2.5	39	25
2017 M	3	41	21	2018 M	3	31	20
2017 M	3	40	19	2018 F	3	44	20
2017 F	3	35	19	2018 M	2	40	15
2017 M	3	45	19	2018 M	2.5	41	14
2017 F	3.5	40	18	2018 F	2.5	40	14
2017 M	2.5	31	16	2018 F	2.5	31	14
2017 M	2	41	15	2018 F	2	33	11
2017 F	2.5	30	14	2018 M	2	34	11
2017 M	2	28	8	2018 M	2	33	10
2017 M	2	34	6	2018 M	1.5	26	4
2017 F	2	32	6				

Munozara

Yapon tili bo'yicha kompetensiyani baholash usullariga doir muammolar

Ushbu tadqiqotda qo'llanilgan yapon tili testlari asosan *yutuq testlari* (ya'ni, ma'lum o'quv mazmuni o'zlashtirilganligini baholovchi testlar) bo'lganligi sababli, talabalarning umumiy kompetensiyasidagi farqlarni aniqlash uchun mos emas edi.

Tashkiliy sabablarga ko'ra, mavjud o'quv dasturiga kiritilgan muntazam imtihon natijalari aynan shu holatda tahlilga kiritildi. Biroq, faqat o'rganilgan mazmuni egallaganlikni emas, balki ayni damdagi yapon tili kompetensiyasining umumiy darajasini aniqlashga xizmat qiladigan maxsus testlarni o'tkazish zarurati ayon bo'ldi.

Kam ball to'plagan guruhda kuzatilgan tendensiyalar

Boshqa tomondan, ayrim qiziqarli tendensiyalar ham kuzatildi. RSTda yuqori ball olgan ishtirokchilar sinovlar davomida barqaror yuqori natijalarni saqlab qoldilar yoki asta-sekin yutuqlarini oshirib bordilar. Aksincha, RSTda past ball olgan guruhda natijalar katta o'zgaruvchanlikni ko'rsatdi, bu esa ularning natijalarini oldindan aytish qiyinligini ko'rsatadi (1-rasm). Bu esa yuqori ball olgan guruh yapon tilini izchil va puxta egallab borayotganini ko'rsatmoqda. Past ball olgan guruh esa, ehtimol, test strategiyalari yordamida vaqtinchalik yaxshi natijalarga erishgan, ammo haqiqiy til kompetensiyasi past darajada qolgan. Ayniqsa, o'rta darajadagi testlarga o'tilganida, past ball olgan guruhda natijalar sezilarli darajada yomonlashgan, yuqori ball olgan guruhda esa bu holat deyarli kuzatilmadi. Bu o'zgarish test formatining o'zgarishi bilan izohlanadi: yangi test shaklida ham yuqori ball guruhining natijalari barqaror qolgan, past ball guruhida esa bu o'zgarish salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Bu natijalar RSTda yuqori

ball olgan guruh tilni chuqurroq egallagan, past ball olganlar esa faqat testlarga tayyorlangan bo'lishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

1-rasm: RSTda yuqori ball to'plagan guruh (chapda) va past ball to'plagan guruh (o'ngda) ishtirokchilarning yapon tili testlari bo'yicha natijalaridagi o'zgarishlar

Xulosa

Mazkur tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, working memory sig'imi bilan yapon tilini o'zlashtirish darajasi o'rtasida sezilarli bog'liqlik aniqlanmadi. Bu natija Malayziyalik yapon tili o'rganuvchilari ustida o'tkazilgan va WM bilan o'qish tushunish qobiliyati o'rtasidagi munosabatni tekshirgan avvalgi tadqiqot natijalari bilan mos keladi. Biroq o'quv jarayoni davomida RSTda yuqori ball to'plagan ishtirokchilar nisbatan barqaror yutuqlarga ega bo'lgan ko'rinadi. Test ballari ba'zan qisqa muddatli tayyorlov, masalan, lug'atni yodlash kabi uslublar orqali yuqori natijalarga olib kelishi mumkin. Past ball to'plagan guruhlar test strategiyalaridan kuchli ta'sirlangan bo'lsa-da, yuqori ball to'plaganlar real til bilimlariga tayanib, test formatidan qat'i nazar, doimiy natijalarga erishgan bo'lishi mumkin.

Har qanday holatda ham, working memory bo'yicha ilmiy yutuqlarni til o'rgatish sohasiga tatbiq etish uchun hali yechilishi kerak bo'lgan bir qator muammolar mavjud. Birinchi navbatda, RST qanday til kompetensiyasini baholayotganini aniq tushuntirib berish lozim. Ayni noaniqlik sababli, ilgari o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarning natijalari va ularning talqinlari bir-biridan sezilarli darajada farq qilmoqda. working memory nazariy doirasini amaliy ta'lim jarayonlariga qanday muvofiqlashtirish mumkinligi masalasi bo'yicha ham hali asosiy tadqiqotlarga ehtiyoj bor. Biroq, agar o'quvchilarning rivojlanish sur'atlarini faqat o'qituvchining tajribasi yoki sezgilariga tayanmasdan, yanada aniqroq bashorat qilish imkoniyati yaratilsa, bu til ta'limi amaliyoti uchun katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuning uchun, RST testining ishonchligi va aniqligini oshirish bilan bir qatorda, working memoryning til o'rganishdagi rolini yanada chuqurroq tahlil qilish zarur. Kelgusida ham psixologiya sohasidagi ilmiy yutuqlarni yapon tili ta'limiga faol tatbiq etish muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi.

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DIN VA TIL: TEOLINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLAR VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI**Otaboyeva Mazmuna Rahimovna**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola teolingvistika, ya'ni din va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganish sohasiga bag'ishlangan. Teolingvistika diniy matnlar, terminologiya va tildagi diniy ma'nolarni tadqiq etadi. Maqola ushbu fanning rivojlanish tarixi, asosiy yo'nalishlari va O'zbekistondagi o'rganishlari haqida ma'lumot beradi. Teolingvistik tadqiqotlarning muqaddas matnlar, diniy nutq va ibodatlarda ishlatiladigan maxsus til, shuningdek, dinning tilga ta'siri kabi muhim jihatlarni ko'rsatadi. O'zbekistonda teolingvistika hali nisbatan yangi bo'lsa-da, diniy va tilshunoslik masalalariga qiziqishning ortishi bu sohaning rivojlanish imkoniyatlarini oshirmoqda. Maqola teolingvistik tadqiqotlarning ahamiyati va kelajakdagi istiqbollari ham yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: teolingvistika, din va til, muqaddas matnlar, diniy terminologiya, ibodat tili, tarjima va tahlil, diniy e'tiqodlar, lingvistik strukturalar, diniy nutq, madaniyatlararo munosabatlar, postkolonial teolingvistika, qiyosiy tahlil.

Abstract: This article is dedicated to the field of theolinguistics, which explores the interrelation between religion and language. Theolinguistics examines religious texts, terminology, and the linguistic expressions of religious meanings. The article provides information on the historical development of this discipline, its main directions, and studies conducted in Uzbekistan. It highlights key aspects of theolinguistic research, such as sacred texts, the specialized language used in religious discourse and worship, and the influence of religion on language. Although theolinguistics is relatively new in Uzbekistan, the growing interest in religious and linguistic issues enhances the potential for its development. The article also discusses the significance of theolinguistic studies and their future prospects.

Keywords: theolinguistics, religion and language, sacred texts, religious terminology, liturgical language, translation and analysis, religious beliefs, linguistic structures, religious discourse, intercultural relations, postcolonial theolinguistics, comparative analysis.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена теолингвистике — научной дисциплине, изучающей взаимосвязь между религией и языком. Теолингвистика исследует религиозные тексты, терминологию и языковые выражения религиозных смыслов. В статье представлена информация об истории развития этой области, её основных направлениях и исследованиях, проводимых в Узбекистане. Особое внимание уделяется таким аспектам, как священные тексты, специализированный язык, используемый в религиозной речи и богослужении, а также влияние религии на язык. Несмотря на относительную новизну теолингвистики в Узбекистане, растущий интерес к религиозным и лингвистическим вопросам способствует её развитию. В статье также рассматривается значимость теолингвистических исследований и их перспективы.

Ключевые слова: теолингвистика, религия и язык, священные тексты, религиозная терминология, язык богослужения, перевод и анализ, религиозные верования, лингвистические структуры, религиозная речь, межкультурные отношения, постколониальная теолингвистика, сравнительный анализ.

Kirish

Teolingvistika (teo- va lingvistika so'zlaridan) — tilshunoslikning din va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganuvchi sohasi. Ushbu fan diniy matnlar, diniy terminologiya va tildagi diniy ma'nolarni tadqiq qiladi. Teolingvistika dinning tilga ta'sirini, turli dinlar orasidagi til farqlarini va diniy e'tiqodlar til rivojiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Shu jumladan, muqaddas matnlar va ulardagi lingvistik strukturalarni tahlil qilish, ibodat va diniy nutq tili bilan shug'ullanadi.

Metodologiya

Teolingvistika 1970-yillarda Evropada lingvistikaning mustaqil sohasi sifatida vujudga keldi. Germaniyadagi Bonn shahrida joylashgan Injil tafsirchisi Edhardt Guttgemanns (1935-2008) ning Yangi Ahd ilohiyotiga umumiy lingvistik tomondan yondashuvi bu sohaning ilk urinishlaridan biridir. 1970 yilda u "Linguistica Biblica" jurnaliga asos soldi, bu jurnal shu paytgacha ilohiyotshunoslik, semiotika, tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslik kabi fanlararo o'zaro almashinuv uchun yagona jurnal bo'lib kelgan (jurnal 1993 yilgacha nashr qilingan). Jurnalning 1976 yilgi nashrida Jan-Pierre van Noppen "teolingvistika" (Theolinguistik) terminini taklif etdi. So'nggi 40 yil

davomida turli mamlakatlardan ko'plab olimlar tomonidan din tili bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borildi. Nemis va polyak teolingvistlari hamkorlikda xalqaro teolingvistlar birlashmasini tashkil qilishdi. Bu guruh tashkil etilganidan buyon har yili til va din masalalarini muhokama qilish uchun konferensiyalar o'tkaziladi. 2008 yildan beri teolingvistlar guruhi "Theolinguistica" jurnalini chop etib kelmoqda. Bu tadqiqotlar asosan xristianlik dini bilan bog'liq.

Natijalar

Teolingvistikaning jahon miqyosida o'rganilishi turli madaniyat va dinlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan boy ilmiy merosga ega. Bu soha din va tilning o'zaro ta'sirini chuqur tahlil qilishga qaratilgan tadqiqotlar orqali keng rivojlanmoqda. Teolingvistika yirik tillarda yozilgan muqaddas matnlar, ibodatlar va diniy nutqlarni o'rganishdan tortib, dunyodagi barcha asosiy dinlar va madaniyatlar bo'yicha lingvistik tadqiqotlar olib boradi. Ushbu soha bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar teolingvistikaning quyidagi asosiy yo'nalishlari sifatida quyidagilarni keltirib o'tilgan.

1. Muqaddas matnlar tarjimasi va lingvistik tahlili: Dunyodagi eng ko'p o'rganilgan teolingvistik mavzulardan biri muqaddas matnlarning tarjimasi va lingvistik tahlilidir. Qur'on, Injil, Tavrod kabi muqaddas kitoblar ko'plab tillarga tarjima qilingan va ularning tarjima jarayoni lingvistlar, dinshunoslar va falsafachilar uchun asosiy tadqiqot ob'ekti bo'lib kelmoqda.

2. Til va din o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir: Turli dinlarda til diniy e'tiqodlarni qanday ifoda qilishi va din tilni qanday shakllantirishi o'rganiladi. Masalan, lotin tili katolik cherkovi an'anasida asosiy ibodat tili bo'lib kelgan.

3. Ibodat va diniy nutq lingvistikasi: Diniy nutq tili odatda oddiy kundalik nutqdan farq qiladi. Jahon miqyosida ibodatlar, marosimlar va diniy xabarlar o'ziga xos til orqali yetkaziladi.

4. Diniy terminologiya va tushunchalar evolyutsiyasi: Jahon dinlarining ko'pchiligida maxsus diniy terminologiya va atamalar tizimi mavjud. Bu atamalarning qanday shakllangani va ularning ma'nolari tarqalganligi o'rganiladi.

5. Postkolonial teolingvistika: Dinning kolonial davrda mahalliy tillarga va madaniyatlarga qanday ta'sir qilganini o'rganadi. Yevropa mustamlakachiligi davrida ko'plab xalq tillari yevropalik missionerlar tomonidan o'rgatilib, diniy til o'zgarishiga sabab bo'ldi.

6. Qiyosiy teolingvistika: Turli dinlar o'rtasidagi lingvistik farqlar va o'xshashliklar o'rganiladi. Islom, Xristianlik va Yahudiylikning diniy tillari va matnlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali ularning tarixiy va lingvistik o'zaro ta'siri chuqur o'rganiladi.

Munozara

O'zbekistonda teolingvistika nisbatan yangi tadqiqot yo'nalishi bo'lib, hali keng rivojlanishi talab etiladigan sohalardan biri hisoblanadi. Biroq, diniy va

tilshunoslik masalalariga qiziqish ortib borayotgani sababli, bu sohaning kelajakda ilmiy tadqiqotlar doirasida rivojlanish imkoniyatlari mavjud.

O'zbekistonda teolingvistikaga oid o'rganishlar bir necha yo'nalishlarda o'z aksini topganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

1. Islom madaniyati va til: O'zbekiston Islom madaniyati markazlaridan biri sifatida ko'p asrlik diniy merosga ega.

2. Tasavvuf adabiyoti va til: O'zbekistonda tasavvuf bilan bog'liq diniy matnlar va adabiy asarlar katta ahamiyatga ega.

3. Diniy matnlar tarjimasi: Qur'on, Hadis va boshqa muqaddas matnlarning o'zbek tiliga tarjimasi yuzasidan ilmiy ishlar amalga oshirilgan.

4. Til va diniy meros: O'zbekistonda diniy merosni o'rganish markazlari va ilmiy muassasalar mavjud.

5. Universitet va ilmiy-tadqiqot markazlari: O'zbekistonning ba'zi universitetlarida tilshunoslik va dinshunoslik bilan bog'liq fanlar o'qitiladi.

Teolingvistika alohida ilmiy yo'nalish sifatida din va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganish imkoniyatlari keng. Islom madaniyati, Qur'on tarjimasi, tasavvuf va diniy adabiyotlar bo'yicha olib borilayotgan ilmiy ishlar teolingvistika uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Teolingvistika dinshunoslik, falsafa va sotsiologiya bilan o'zaro bog'liq bo'lib, jamiyatdagi til va dinning o'rnini haqida chuqur bilim beradi. Bu soha orqali turli dinlar va madaniyatlar til nuqtai nazaridan qiyosiy tahlil qilinishi mumkin.

Teolingvistika tilshunoslikning alohida sohasi sifatida o'z oldiga bir nechta savollarni qo'yadi. Masalan, Qanday qilib muqaddas matnlar tarjima qilinadi va bu jarayonda ma'no qanday o'zgaradi? Ushbu savolga quyidagicha javob berish mumkin.

Muqaddas matnlar tarjima jarayoni ko'plab omillarga bog'liq. Ushbu jarayonda asarlarning tarixiy, madaniy va lingvistik kontekstini hisobga olish juda muhim. Tarjima jarayonida quyidagi omillar ma'no o'zgarishiga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin:

1. **Til va grammatik tuzilmalar:** Har bir tilning o'ziga xos grammatikasi va sintaksisi mavjud. Tarjimon bu farqlarni hisobga olib, muqaddas matnni o'z tilida ravon va tushunarli qilib ifodalashi kerak.

2. **Madaniy kontekst:** Muqaddas matnlar ko'pincha o'z zamonining madaniyatiga va ijtimoiy sharoitlariga bog'liq bo'ladi. Tarjimon ushbu kontekstni inobatga olmasligi, matnning asl ma'nosini o'zgartirishi mumkin.

3. **Ishoratlar va tasvirlar:** Ba'zi iboralar yoki tasvirlar bir tilni boshqasiga tarjima qilganda o'z ma'nosini yo'qotishi yoki tushunarsiz bo'lishi mumkin. Tarjimon ushbu qiyinchiliklarni engib o'tish uchun izohlar kiritishi yoki alternativ iboralardan foydalanishi kerak.

4. **Ishonchli manbaalar:** Tarjima jarayonida original matnni to'g'ri tushunish uchun bir nechta ishonchli manbaalardan foydalanish muhimdir. Tarjimonlar ko'pincha

turli xil tafsirlar va izohli nashrlardan foydalangan holda asarning ma'no qatlamlarini ochishga harakat qiladilar.

5. O'zgartirishlar va yangilanishlar: Tarjima jarayonida matnning ma'nosi va talqini vaqt o'tishi bilan o'zgarishi mumkin. Yangi tushunchalar yoki ijtimoiy kontekstlar eski matnlarga yangi ma'no berishi mumkin.

Muqaddas matnlarning tarjimasi har doim murakkab va ko'p qatlamli jarayon bo'lib, uning natijasi ko'pincha asl matnning o'zgarishini va yangi ma'nolarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

- Diniy nutq va oddiy nutq orasidagi farqlar nimalarda namoyon bo'ladi? Diniy nutq va oddiy nutq orasidagi farqlar bir qator jihatlarda namoyon bo'ladi:

1. **Maqsad:** Diniy nutq ko'pincha ma'naviy, etik yoki ruhiy o'zgarishlarni, o'g'itlarni berish maqsadida ishlatiladi. Oddiy nutq esa kundalik muloqot va axborot almashish uchun qulay va oddiy usuldir.

2. **Til va leksika:** Diniy nutqda maxsus terminologiya va iboralar, shuningdek, diniy matnlardan olingan so'zlar ko'proq qo'llaniladi. Oddiy nutqda esa sodda va tushunarli til, umumiy so'zlar ishlatiladi.

3. **Uslub:** Diniy nutq ko'pincha rituallarga, ta'limotlarga yoki qadimiy an'analarga asoslanadi va ko'proq formal uslubga ega. Oddiy nutqda esa ko'proq erkin va norasmiy uslubga ega bo'ladi.

4. **Qayta ishlash va strukturaviy jihatlar:** Diniy nutq ko'pincha muayyan struktura, masalan, o'qish, ibodat yoki taqdimot shaklida bo'ladi. Oddiy nutq esa erkin va fleksibil, aniq tuzilmasiz bo'lishi mumkin.

5. **Mavzular:** Diniy nutqda odatda ruhiy, axloqiy va ilohiy mavzular muhokama qilinadi, oddiy nutqda esa kundalik hayot, ish, oila va boshqa oddiy mavzular yoritiladi.

6. **Auditoriya:** Diniy nutq ma'lum bir jamoa yoki diniy guruh uchun mo'ljallangan bo'lishi mumkin. Oddiy nutq esa kengroq auditoriyaga, har qanday odam bilan muloqot qilish uchun xizmat qiladi.

Ushbu farqlar diniy nutqni ko'proq ijtimoiy va madaniy kontekstdan ajratib turadi, shuningdek, odamlarning qanday muloqot qilishi va qabul qilishi bilan bog'liq bo'ladi.

- Turli dinlarda til orqali qaysi asosiy g'oyalar tarqatiladi?

Turli dinlarda til orqali tarqatiladigan asosiy g'oyalar quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

1. **Ilohiyning mavjudligi:** Diniy matnlar va ta'limotlar orqali ilohiy mavjudlik, uning xususiyatlari va inson hayotidagi roli haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi. Bu g'oyalar ko'pincha ishonch, ibodat va taqvo haqida.

2. **Axloqiy qadriyatlar:** Dinlar ko'pincha axloqiy me'yorlar va qadriyatlarni belgilaydi, masalan, yaxshilik qilish, adolat, sabr-toqat, va o'zaro yordam berish kabi g'oyalarni ilgari suradi.

3. **Hayot va o'lim:** Diniy ta'limotlar hayotning ma'nosi, o'lim va hayotdan keyingi hayot haqida g'oyalarni o'z ichiga oladi, bu esa odamlarning hayotga bo'lgan munosabatini shakllantiradi.

4. **Jamoatchilik va ijtimoiy mas'uliyat:** Diniy nutq jamoaviy qadriyatlarni, birlikni va ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni tarqatadi. Jamoa ichidagi aloqalar va bir-biriga yordam berish, dinlarning muhim g'oyalaridan biridir.

5. **Ritual va an'analar:** Diniy til orqali rituallar, ibodatlar va an'analar haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Bu, shuningdek, insonlarning diniy hayotiga qanday kirishishi va ularni qanday amalga oshirishlari haqida.

6. **Ruhiy o'sish va o'zini anglash:** Dinlar ko'pincha insonni o'z ichki dunyosini o'rganishga, ruhiy o'sishga va o'zini anglashga yo'naltiruvchi g'oyalarni ilgari suradi.

7. **Maqsad va vazifalar:** Diniy g'oyalar, insonlarning hayotdagi maqsadlari va vazifalarini belgilaydi, bu esa ularni ruhiy va axloqiy jihatdan yo'naltirishga yordam beradi.

Ushbu g'oyalar turli dinlarda xilma-xil shaklda, lekin umuman olganda insoniyatning asosiy savollariga javob berishga intilmoqda.

Xulosa

Teolingvistika dinshunoslik, falsafa va sotsiologiya bilan o'zaro bog'liq bo'lib, jamiyatdagi til va dinning o'rnini haqida chuqur bilim beradi. Bu soha orqali turli dinlar va madaniyatlar til nuqtai nazaridan qiyosiy tahlil qilinishi mumkin. Teolingvistikaning rivojlanishi, ayniqsa, O'zbekistonda ilmiy tadqiqotlar va xalqaro konferensiyalar orqali yanada kengayishi kutilmoqda.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktab ta'limida chet tilini o'rganish va zamonaviy dunyoda uning inson hayotidagi o'rni va ro'li, ajralmas qismga aylanayotganligi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, chet tillari-bu faqat so'zlar to'plami emas, balki dunyo bilan aloqa vositasi ekanligi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tili, Chet tilining maqsadlari, o'g'zaki nutq, tarbiyaviy maqsad, qaror va farmonlar, darslik, metodlar.

Annotation: This article analyzes the process of learning foreign languages in school education and explores its role and significance in modern life. It also emphasizes that a foreign language is not merely a collection of words but a vital means of effective communication with the world. The educational and communicative goals of language learning, as well as the importance of textbooks, teaching methods, and regulatory documents, are also discussed.

Keywords: foreign language, educational objectives, oral speech, educational approach, decrees and regulations, textbook, teaching methods.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется процесс изучения иностранных языков в школьном образовании и его значение в современной жизни. Подчеркивается, что иностранный язык — это не просто набор слов, а важнейшее средство эффективного общения с окружающим миром. Также рассматриваются образовательные и коммуникативные цели обучения, роль учебников, методов преподавания и нормативных документов.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, цели обучения, устная речь, воспитательная цель, постановления и указы, учебник, методы обучения.

Hammamizga ma'lumki hozirgi kunda maktab ta'lim tizimida chet-tillarini chuqur o'rganish va samarali o'rgatishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu jumladan: ingliz tili, rus tili, turk tili va arab tillarini o'rganishga bo'lgan ehtiyoj yuqorilab bormoqda. Bu tillarni o'rganish orqali davlatning urf-odatlarini, milliy madaniyatlarini hamda tarixini o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishni uyg'otadi.

Bu esa bevosita maktab bosqichidan boshlanishi zarur. Maktab o'quvchisining bugungi bilim va ko'nikmalari ertanggi kuning poydevoridir.

Chet tili o'qitishning umumta'limiy maqsadi. O'quvchilarga chet tili uchunchi til sifatida o'rgatiladi. Majburiy o'quv predmetlaridan biri bo'lmish chet tili, boshqa fanlar qatorida umumiy ta'lim berishda o'z ulushini qo'shadi. Chet til o'rganish natijasi ham, jarayoni ham, umumta'limiy ahamiyatga molikdir, chunki chet tili vositasida olinadigan axborotdan tashqari, uni o'rganish jarayonida qo'llanadigan til birliklari

tafakkurini rivojlantiradi, nutqning ifoda planidagi yangi hodisalar o'quvchilar uchun qiziqarli bo'lib, ularning til tajribasini boyitadi.

▪ **Til o'rganishning ilk bosqichi:** leksik, grammatik va talaffuz birliklarini og'zaki nutq jarayonida o'zlashtirishga ko'proq e'tibor qaratiladi.

▪ **Yuqori bosqichida:** chet tilidagi grafik va audiomatndan axborot yig'ish o'quvchilarda hayotiy yangiliklarni bilish ishtiyoqini kuchaytiradi.

Chet tilini o'qitishda tarbiyaviy maqsadi. Til materiallarida tarbiyaviy jihatdan foydalanish hisoblanadi. Masalan, o'zaro chet tilida og'zaki muloqat chog'ida suhbatdoshiga hurmat bilan qarash, odob doirasiga kiradigan so'z va iboralarni qo'llash (rahmat, marhamat, qiling kabilar) birgalashib she'rlar, dialoglar aytish, o'zi va sheriklari xatti-harakatini odob bilan chet tilida sharhlay olish singari gaplar o'quvchini madaniyat sari yetaklaydi.

▪ **Yorqin va ilmiy ifoda shakli:** olinadigan yangilik-malumotlar tarbiyalashning tengi yo'q metodik vositalaridandir. Matnlar mazmuni dastur nutq mavzulariga mos kelishi hamda o'quvchilarning ma'naviy ehtiyojini qondirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi talab qilinadi.

Darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda, to'garak ishlarida, chet til xonasida uyushtiriladigan o'quv tadbirlar jaryonida ham tarbiyaviy maqsad amalga oshirib boriladi. Chet til o'qitishning rivojlatiruvchi maqsadi. O'quvchi shaxsining aqliy, hissiy va motivatsion tarafini rivojlantirishni ifodalay boshlaydi. Chet tili o'qitishda o'quvchilarning aqliy saviyasini quyidan yuqoriga ko'tarish, aqliy jihatdan ravnaq toptirish, mazmunan yuksaltirish ijobiy ma'noda aqlan yanada ulg'ayishini ta'minlaydi. Ushbu maqsadning ro'yobga chiqishi ko'zlangan. O'quvchilarning oldiga qo'yiladigan chet tili o'qitish maqsadlarining qisqacha tushunchasi.

▪ **Amaliy maqsad:** Chet tilida muloqat yurutish, yani bular gapirish, tinglab tushunish, o'qish va yozishni o'rgatish.

▪ **Ta'limi maqsad:** Xotira va mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish, o'quvchilar bilim saviyasini va umumiy madaniyatni yuksaltirish.

▪ **Tarbiyaviy maqsad:** G'oyaviy-siyosiy tarbiya, aqliy mehnat malakalarini hosil qilish, o'quvchilarning bilim faoliyatini oshirish.

▪ **Rivojlantiruvchi maqsad:** O'quvchi shaxsining aqliy, hissiy va motivatsion xususiyatarini rivojlantirishdir.

Shuningdek yurtimizda til o'rganishga bo'lgan e'tibor nuqtai nazaridan ham oladigan bo'sak aynan yaqin 5-10 yil davomida misli ko'rinmagan ishlar amalga oshirildi va buni siyosat darajasiga olib chiqishdi. Bu borada davlatimiz rahbari Sh.M.Mirziyoyev farmonlari va Oliy Majlis chiqarayotgan qaror va qonunlar hamda ularni amalga oshirish uchun Vazirlar Mahkamasi tomondan qilinayotgan chora tadbirlar katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ta'lim sohasini tubdan chet tillariga tatbiq qilish maqsadida taqdim etilayotgan darsliklar o'quv qo'llanmalari ham ayni shu maqsadning

amaliy isbotidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2021-yil 19-maydagi 312-sonli Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishni, ommalashtirishni samarali tashkil etish chora tadbirlari to'g'risidagi qaroriga ko'ra xorijiy tillarni nafaqat ta'limda, balki davlat organlari xodimlari ham bilishi kerakligi va ularda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish va o'rgatish yuzasidan bir qancha chora tadbirlar ishlab chiqilmoqda. Chet tili ayniqsa, ingliz tilini o'rganish yoki bilish-ilmiy muloqotlarni, biznes dunyosini ma'daniy aloqalarini va siyosiy muamolarini bilishda muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Chet tilini bilish hayot davomida muvaffaqiyat kaliti ekanligi ko'pchilik tomonidan tan olinadi. Motivatsiya hamda munosabat chet tilini o'rganuvchi o'quvchilarda ishonchini uyg'otib, tilini tez va samarali tarzda o'rganishiga yordam beradi. Shuning uchun, chet tilini o'rgatuvchi pedagoglar mana shu faktorlarni inobatga olishi zarur.

Yana bir qarorga ko'ra, Vazirlar Mahkamasining " Oliy ta'lim muassalariga o'qishga qabul qilishda milliy hamda xalqaro baholash tizmlari sertifikatlarini tatbiq qilish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 2019-yil 13-maydagi 395-son qarori bilan belgilangan " Davlat test markazi tomonidan beriladigon chet tilini bilish darajasi to'g'risidagi sertifikat, keyingi o'rinlarda- milliy sertifikat yoki xalqaro tan olgan sertifikatning tegishli darajalariga ega bo'lgan abituriyentlarga o'qishga kirish sinovlarida berilgan imtiyozlar saqlab qolinadi. Chet tili fanidan kasbiy-ijodiy kirish imtihonlari Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Davlat test Markazi tomonidan amalga oshiriladi.

Olimlarni qarashlari

Chet tilini o'rganish bo'yicha Gardner fikriga ko'ra, "Shaxs chet tilini o'rganishga bo'lgan istagi paydo bo'lsagina va bu inson chet tilini o'rganishga intilishidan dalolat beradi" deb aytadi. Oksford tahriridagi lug'atlarda motivatsiyaga nisbatan ta'rif berilgan. "Bir kishining harakatlari yoki xatti-harakatlarida namoyon bo'lishi sifatida ta'rif berilgan". Motivatsiya mavhum tushuncha hisoblanib, motivatsiyani aniqlash qiyinchilik tug'diradi. Motivatsiya orqali chet tilini o'rganuvchi o'quvchilar ajralib turadi, chunki ularda chet tilini o'rganishda ishtiyoqi baland bo'lganligi va ular chet tilini o'zlashtirishda yaxshiroq natijaga erishishi bilan ko'rinib turadi.

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytganda, binobarin o'z ona tilisiga qiziqqan va puxta o'rgangan o'quvchigina boshqa tillarga mehr ko'yib o'rgana oladi. Til bu millatlar o'rtasida ko'prik vazifasini o'tovchi vosita undan qo'rqmay hatlab o'tganlar yutuq va yangi olamlar kalitini qo'lga kiritadi. Chet tillarini o'rganish davomida innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish natijasida o'quvchilarning darsga bo'lgan qiziqishlari ortadi va darslarni o'zlashtirish osonlashadi. Chet tilini o'rganish uchun hozirgi kunda ko'plab shart-sharoitlar yaratilgan. Ayniqsa bundan yoshlarimiz oqilona foydalanishlari kerak, chet tillarini bilish insonni har tomonlama yuksaltiradi.

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Sociolinguistic analysis of bilingual students

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Annotation: This article offers a sociolinguistic examination of bilingual students to uncover pedagogical implications for optimizing their learning experiences, analyzing language use, social dynamics, and learning contexts across various linguistic subgroups, the study reveals critical insights into the factors that shape bilingual student success, advocating for tailored instructional approaches and classroom practices that leverage students' linguistic and cultural resources to promote academic achievement and linguistic competence.

Keywords: Sociolinguistics, bilingual students, language use, social identity, learning outcomes, educational context, linguistic subgroups, pedagogical implications, inclusive education, effective learning.

Аннотация: Данная статья предлагает социолингвистическое исследование двуязычных студентов с целью выявления педагогических последствий для оптимизации их учебного опыта. Анализируя использование языка, социальную динамику и учебные контексты в различных языковых подгруппах, исследование раскрывает важные сведения о факторах, формирующих успех двуязычных студентов. В статье отстаиваются адаптированные методы обучения и практические занятия в классе, которые используют лингвистические и культурные ресурсы студентов для повышения их успеваемости и языковой компетентности.

Keywords: Ключевые слова: Социолингвистика, двуязычные студенты, использование языка, социальная идентичность, результаты обучения, образовательный контекст, языковые подгруппы, педагогические последствия, инклюзивное образование, эффективное обучение.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ikki tilli talabalarni ijtimoiy lingvistik jihatdan o'rganishni taklif etadi, bu esa ularning o'rganish tajribalarini optimallashtirish uchun pedagogik oqibatlarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Turli lingvistik subguruhlar bo'yicha til ishlatish, ijtimoiy dinamikalar va o'rganish kontekstlarini tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot ikki tilli talabalar muvaffaqiyatini shakllantiruvchi omillar haqida muhim ma'lumotlarni ochib beradi. Bu, talabalar til va madaniy resurslaridan foydalanishga asoslangan moslashtirilgan ta'lim yondashuvlari va dars amaliyotlarini

qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, bu esa akademik muvaffaqiyat va til kompetensiyasini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy lingvistika, ikki tilli talabalar, til ishlatish, ijtimoiy identitet, o'rganish natijalari, ta'lim konteksti, lingvistik subguruhlar, pedagogik oqibatlar, inklyuziv ta'lim, samarali o'rganish.

Introduction

Informing about group of learners, Agrarian university where unites the students to study in a location and I work here as an English teacher to 1st year students. There are 16 students whose ages are the same (19) but the representatives of different nations such as Russian, Turkish and Uzbek (native) in my English classes. Although their ages are at the same, they are on 2 levels such as pre-intermediate and intermediate. There are 3 representatives of nations namely, 4 Russian learners and 2 of them are girls and the other is a boy, 3 girls from Turkey and the rest 4 are boys and 5 Uzbek girls.

Subgroups

First subgroup (A) includes Russian ESL learners (English is a second language). Russian students used to learn English when they were at the age of school. They are aware of not only Russian and English but also Turkish as well. They learned the language from watching movies and listening to music in Turkish language. Unfortunately, they are not able to speak in Uzbek but can understand some words in this language. When it comes to their socioeconomic status, they are from poor class family whose parents are not able to purchase necessary course paper based on the lessons during the learning process. Thus, they are always provided with course materials by university itself. Learners from second subgroup (B) are the representatives of Istanbul of Turkey who had moved there a year ago with their families. There are the children of mixed nations namely, either their mothers or fathers are Turkish who came from wealthy family and have no any financial problems on buying needed course materials for the class. However, their clothing and hair style do not look like to other students'. In other words, they wear very tight and short clothes, and their unusual hair color attracts everyone's attention in the group. Moreover, boys' and girls' attitudes to each other are not associated with another students, they hug when a boy and a girl see each other and it brings opposite opinions to other nations students according to their religious beliefs.

Learning context

In terms of *learning context*, since I am a teacher at Agrarian university, where lessons are organized in it. The lessons are taught mostly in English but if Russian learners cannot translate some words into English, Russian language can be used and the same way for Turkish students but Uzbek may be used to translate English words for them. English is planned to teach 2 semesters in a year in the outline of the schedule

of the university. As there are different nationalities in the class, teacher conducts interactive and collaborative activities in order to unite them and create friendly atmosphere. In other words, there are many activities such as group discussions, group working or peer work which present their activeness in a group. Moreover, I prefer to conduct a survey which asks about the points students struggle with and their strength and it helps me to use and find a way or method such as TBLT, Sheltered or Audio-lingual for learners to improve their weaknesses. They are quite old to impress what they want or need in their future learning process. **Race and ethnicity, identity** show a huge impact to the learning process. As there are different nation representatives in the group, they have unsimilar family and cultural backgrounds. Not only their minds but also appearances distinguish from each other Russian students prefer to wear clothes that they consider comfortable, but this causes a negative attitude towards them from the point of view of education in some Uzbek and Turkish learners in terms of some rules of Islam region. However, while Russian and Turkish learners are brought up to express their opinion freely in public without fear or hesitation, Uzbek learners are shy to ask about a part they do not understand and often remain silent. Turkish students prefer to wear clothes that they consider comfortable, but this causes a negative attitude towards Turkish students from the point of view of education in some Uzbek learners. Actually, religious minds and background should not be taught in the class, but as they all are the children of the Muslims' they must be followed to the sociocultural framework of the location in the class. Sexuality is not taught in the class because of not being relevant.

Pedagogical implication.

Conducting activities suitable for representatives of all nationalities is the main goal of pedagogical implication. It is important for me as a teacher to be able to choose appropriate tasks or activities and use methods to unite them so that none of the representatives of several nationalities in the group feel discriminated by their appearance, ethics, or race. For example, conducting discussions on various topics such as friendship, kindness and helping others through group working or peer working will help them understand the topic and communicate unitedly. The main reason of focusing more on communicating is to prevent the wrong English accent of the learners due to their L1 and their region and to ensure fluent and accurate output. Due to the fact that their region and nations are different, they have different pronunciations in one word. The biggest help in correcting pronunciation is to have it heard by natives. Technical devices in the classroom play a big role in this process.

Linguistic assessment

There are different assessing methods here, but not all of them are always suitable. For example, tests written on paper or methods that require only the translation of words may not be able to show the language potential of the student. That

is, taking the assessment part with both written and oral creativity reveals their weak and strong points in the language. This can show the teacher to focus more on which skill or part of which student. Critical thinking has already developed satisfactorily in almost all students. Their big problem is pronunciation and their ability to actively use grammar that do not exist in their L1 but English includes. However, the traditional method is not a proper assessing way to eliminate the weak points in each of the different subjects.

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A Scientific Analysis of Current Global Economic Trends

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Abstract:

The global economy is undergoing a complex transformation driven by multiple interrelated factors, including the post-pandemic recovery, rising inflationary pressures, and technological advancements. This study presents a scientific analysis of recent economic trends, focusing on empirical data and theoretical frameworks. Using contemporary economic articles and reports as primary sources, the research explores the dynamics of inflation, global recovery, and the role of technological innovation in shaping future economic outcomes. The analysis highlights the uncertainty introduced by geopolitical tensions and suggests strategies for policymakers to mitigate risks and foster sustainable growth.

Аннотация:

Мировая экономика переживает многогранную трансформацию под воздействием взаимодействующих факторов: восстановления после пандемии, роста инфляционного давления и стремительного технологического прогресса. В данном исследовании представлен научный анализ современных экономических тенденций с использованием эмпирических данных и устоявшихся теоретических подходов. На основе актуальных экономических публикаций и отчетов рассматриваются динамика инфляции, траектория глобального восстановления и ключевая роль технологических инноваций в формировании будущих экономических условий. Особое внимание уделяется возросшей неопределенности, вызванной геополитической напряженностью, а также предлагаются стратегические рекомендации для государственных органов по снижению рисков и обеспечению устойчивого экономического роста.

Annotatsiya:

Global iqtisodiyot pandemiyadan keyingi tiklanish, inflyatsiya bosimining oshishi va texnologik rivojlanish kabi bir-biri bilan bog'liq omillar ta'sirida murakkab transformatsiyani boshdan kechirmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqot zamonaviy iqtisodiy tendensiyalarni empirik ma'lumotlar va shakllangan nazariy yondashuvlar asosida ilmiy tahlil qiladi. Amaldagi iqtisodiy maqolalar va hisobotlarga tayangan holda, inflyatsiya dinamikasi, global tiklanish yo'nalishi va texnologik innovatsiyalarning kelajakdagi iqtisodiy muhitni shakllantirishdagi hal qiluvchi roli o'rganiladi. Shuningdek, geosiyosiy tangliklar tufayli yuzaga kelgan noaniqlik muammosi yoritilib, xavflarni kamaytirish va barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashga qaratilgan siyosiy strategiyalar taklif etiladi.

Keywords: Economic Recovery, Inflation, Monetary Policy, COVID-19, Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery, Global Economy, Risks and Uncertainties, technological advancement, Solow growth model.

Kalit so'zlar: Iqtisodiy tiklanish, inflyatsiya, monetar siyosat, COVID-19, pandemiyadan keyingi iqtisodiy tiklanish, global iqtisodiyot, xavf va noaniqliklar, texnologik taraqqiyot, Solou o'sish modeli.

Ключевые слова: Экономическое восстановление, инфляция, денежно-кредитная политика, COVID-19, постпандемическое экономическое восстановление, глобальная экономика, риски и неопределенности, технологические достижения, модель роста Солоу.

Introduction:

The global economy has been significantly impacted by a series of interconnected events, most notably the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical instability, and technological transformation. Economic articles and news from this period reflect a complex interplay of recovery efforts, inflationary pressures, and the continued evolution of digital technologies. Understanding these phenomena requires an integrated approach that combines empirical evidence with economic theory. This study aims to provide insights into the potential long-term effects of these trends on global economic stability and growth.

Methods:

To analyze the current global economic environment, this study employs a mixed-method approach combining qualitative analysis of recent economic articles, quantitative data from central banks and international organizations, and theoretical frameworks from macroeconomic and economic growth models. Key data sources include:

1. International Monetary Fund (IMF) reports on global growth projections and inflation forecasts.
2. OECD data on economic recovery patterns and disparities between developed and developing economies.
3. Recent empirical studies on inflationary pressures and technological innovation in various sectors.

Relevant theoretical models such as the Phillips Curve, Okun's Law, and Solow Growth Model are used to interpret data trends.

Results:**1. Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery**

- The COVID-19 pandemic induced a massive global recession, followed by a partial recovery in many economies. According to recent IMF reports (2024), global GDP growth is projected to return to pre-pandemic levels, but recovery rates vary significantly across regions.

- Advanced economies have benefitted from government stimulus programs, vaccine rollouts, and resilient healthcare systems, while developing economies struggle with vaccine accessibility, external debt burdens, and weaker public health infrastructures.

- Disruptions in global supply chains, particularly in sectors such as semiconductors, energy, and agriculture, further exacerbate economic disparities.

2. Inflation and Monetary Policy

- Data from central banks indicate that inflation rates in 2024 have reached levels not seen in decades, attributed to supply chain disruptions, rising commodity prices, and increased demand.

- The Phillips Curve traditionally describes an inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment; however, recent trends suggest inflation can persist even in low-unemployment environments.

- Policymakers have responded by raising interest rates, yet concerns remain about potential slowdowns in economic growth, particularly in emerging markets with high external debt.

3. Technological Innovation and Economic Transformation

- Accelerated adoption of digital technologies, including AI, blockchain, and renewable energy solutions, is reshaping market dynamics.

- According to the Solow Growth Model, technological progress is a critical factor in long-term economic growth, as it enhances productivity and efficiency across industries.

- AI-driven automation is increasing productivity but also raising concerns about labor market displacement and income inequality.

4. Geopolitical Risks and Global Trade Dynamics

- The Russia-Ukraine war and U.S.-China trade disputes have significantly influenced global trade and investment flows.

- Energy markets have been impacted by ongoing conflicts, leading to increased oil and gas prices and a reassessment of global energy strategies.

- Supply chain disruptions have prompted companies to consider reshoring or nearshoring operations, leading to shifts in manufacturing patterns with long-term economic implications.

Discussion:

The findings highlight that while advanced economies have made substantial strides in recovering from the pandemic, developing nations face ongoing challenges that could result in increased economic inequality. Inflation remains a persistent challenge, and central banks must balance monetary policies to control inflation without stalling economic growth. Technological innovation, particularly in AI, automation, and renewable energy, presents both opportunities and challenges. While these advancements enhance productivity and create new industries, they also pose risks related to labor market disruptions and income inequality. Policymakers must address these issues by investing in education, digital infrastructure, and sustainable energy solutions. Geopolitical risks continue to influence global trade and energy security. International cooperation will be crucial to ensuring the equitable distribution of economic recovery and technological advancements.

Conclusion:

The global economy is currently navigating a period of significant transformation. Inflation, geopolitical risks, and supply chain disruptions create substantial uncertainty. However, ongoing recovery efforts, technological advancements, and sustainability initiatives offer hope for a more resilient economic future. Policymakers, businesses, and individuals must adapt to these changes and leverage innovation to navigate through uncertainty.

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MADANIY-PRAGMATIK REALIYALARNING TARJIMADA QAYTA KODLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI: ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV

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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada badiiy tarjimada madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning qayta kodlanish masalalari zamonaviy tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qilinadi. Tarjima jarayonida realiyalarni saqlash, o'zgartirish yoki moslashtirish strategiyalarining pragmatik maqsadga muvofiqligi o'rganiladi. O'zbek va ingliz tillaridan olingan misollar asosida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning funksional ekvivalentligini ta'minlashning samarali usullari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarjimonning madaniy-pragmatik kompetensiyasi realiyalarni muvaffaqiyatli qayta kodlashning muhim sharti ekanligi asoslanadi. Maqolada taklif etilgan yondashuvlar tarjima amaliyotida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning tarjima tiliga o'tkazilishi samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy-pragmatik realiyalar, pragmatik transfer, qayta kodlash, tarjima strategiyalari, funksional ekvivalentlik, tarjimonning madaniy kompetensiyasi.

Abstract:

This article analyzes the issues of recoding cultural-pragmatic realia in literary translation from the perspective of modern linguistics. The pragmatic appropriateness of strategies for preserving, modifying, or adapting realia in the translation process is examined. Based on examples from Uzbek and English languages, effective methods for ensuring functional equivalence of cultural-pragmatic realia are considered. It is substantiated that the translator's cultural-pragmatic competence is an essential condition for successful recoding of realia. The approaches proposed in the article serve to increase the effectiveness of transferring cultural-pragmatic realia into the target language in translation practice.

Keywords: Cultural-pragmatic realia, pragmatic transfer, recoding, translation strategies, functional equivalence, translator's cultural competence.

Аннотация:

В данной статье анализируются вопросы перекодирования культурно-прагматических реалий в художественном переводе с точки зрения современной лингвистики. Исследуется прагматическая целесообразность стратегий сохранения, изменения или адаптации реалий в процессе перевода. На основе примеров из узбекского и английского языков рассматриваются эффективные способы обеспечения функциональной эквивалентности культурно-прагматических реалий. Обосновывается, что культурно-прагматическая компетенция переводчика является важным условием успешного перекодирования реалий. Предложенные в статье подходы служат повышению эффективности передачи культурно-прагматических реалий на язык перевода в переводческой практике.

Ключевые слова: культурно-прагматические реалии, прагматический трансфер, перекодирование, стратегии перевода, функциональная эквивалентность, культурная компетенция переводчика.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik fanlari rivojining hozirgi bosqichida pragmatik omillarning ahamiyati tobora ortib bormoqda. Tarjima nazariyasida pragmatik yondashuvning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi natijasida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning tarjimadagi talqini alohida tadqiqot yo'nalishiga aylandi. Xususan, bu masalaning dolzarbligi, birinchi navbatda, jahon miqyosida madaniyatlararo muloqotning jadallashuvi, xalqaro aloqalarning barcha sohalarda kengayishi bilan bog'liq. Shu nuqtai nazardan, badiiy matnlarda uchraydigan madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning tarjimada qayta kodlanish xususiyatlarini o'rganish nafaqat nazariy, balki amaliy ahamiyatga ega masala hisoblanadi.

Madaniy-pragmatik realiyalar deganda biz ma'lum bir xalq yoki etnik guruh madaniyatiga xos bo'lgan, boshqa tillarda aniq ekvivalenti bo'lmagan predmetlar, hodisalar, urf-odatlar va tushunchalarni ifodalaydigan so'z va iboralarni tushunamiz. Vlaxov va Florinning ta'kidlashicha, "realiyalar — bu ma'lum bir xalqning turmush tarzini, madaniyatini, ijtimoiy va tarixiy taraqqiyotini aks ettiruvchi so'zlar bo'lib, boshqa xalqlar uchun begona hisoblanadi va shuning uchun ularning tilida to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ekvivalentlari mavjud emas" (Vlaxov & Florin, 1980). Bu ta'rifga asoslanib, madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning tarjimada qayta kodlanish jarayoni murakkab va ko'p qirrali ekanligini ta'kidlash lozim.

Tarjima jarayonida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlash strategiyalarini tanlash tarjimondan nafaqat lingvistik, balki madaniy kompetensiyani ham talab qiladi. Madaniy realiyalarni o'z-o'zidan tushunilmaydigan hodisa sifatida qaraydigan bo'lsak, tarjimon nafaqat so'zlarni, balki ular orqali ifodalanadigan madaniy va pragmatik ma'nolarni ham tarjima qilishi kerak. Aynan shu nuqtada tarjimaning pragmatik jihatlari ustuvor ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Newmark o'zining "A Textbook of Translation" (1988) asarida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni tarjima qilishning beshta asosiy usulini taklif qiladi: transliteratsiya yoki transkripsiya, kalka, funktsional analog, tavsifiy tarjima va izoh berish. Har bir strategiyaning o'z afzalliklari va kamchiliklari mavjud bo'lib, ularni qo'llash kontekstga bog'liq. Masalan, o'zbek tilidagi "palov", "to'y", "gap" kabi so'zlar ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinganda, tarjimon qaysi strategiyaning qo'llashi maqsadga muvofiq?

O'zbek adabiyotidan olingan misollarni tahlil qilish asosida biz madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlashning quyidagi tamoyillarini ajratib ko'rsatishimiz mumkin. Birinchidan, tarjima qilinayotgan realiyaning asl matnda bajarayotgan pragmatik funktsiyasini aniqlab olish zarur. Ikkinchidan, tarjima tilining imkoniyatlarini va o'quvchining madaniy kompetensiyasini hisobga olish lozim. Uchinchidan, tanlangan strategiya tarjima matnining umumiy uslubiga mos kelishi kerak.

O'zbek yozuvchisi Abdulla Qodiriyning "O'tgan kunlar" romanidagi madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning ingliz tiliga tarjimasini tahlil qilish natijasida qiziqarli xulosalarga kelish mumkin. Romanda "chopon", "mahram", "qozilik", "o'rda" kabi o'zbek madaniyati bilan bog'liq ko'plab realiyalar uchraydi. Ushbu realiyalarning ingliz tiliga tarjimasida turli strategiyalar qo'llanilgan. Masalan, "chopon" so'zi ingliz tiliga "chapan" (transliteratsiya) va "traditional Uzbek robe" (tavsifiy tarjima) usullari bilan qayta kodlangan. "Mahram" so'zi esa "confidant" (funktsional analog) sifatida tarjima qilingan. Bu misollar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tarjimon asl matndagi realiyaning pragmatik funktsiyasini va kontekstual mohiyatini hisobga olgan holda, tarjima strategiyasini tanlashi muhim.

Venuti (1995) taklif qilgan "xorijiyashtirish" (foreignization) va "mahalliyashtirish" (domestication) kontseptsiyalari ham madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlash strategiyalarini tushunishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. "Xorijiyashtirish" strategiyasi asl matndagi madaniy o'ziga xoslikni saqlashga qaratilgan bo'lib, tarjima jarayonida realiyalar transkripsiya yoki transliteratsiya orqali saqlanadi. "Mahalliyashtirish" strategiyasi esa, aksincha, asl matndagi madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni tarjima tili madaniyatiga moslashtirish orqali o'quvchiga tushunarli qilishga qaratilgan. Har ikkala strategiyaning o'z o'rni va ahamiyati mavjud bo'lib, ularni to'g'ri tanlash va qo'llash tarjimonning mahoratiga bog'liq.

Madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlashda kontekstual-pragmatik omillarning ahamiyati katta. Nida (1964) ta'kidlaganidek, tarjimada ekvivalentlikka erishish uchun nafaqat lingvistik jihatlar, balki madaniy va pragmatik jihatlar ham hisobga olinishi kerak. Shu nuqtai nazardan, madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlashda tarjimon quyidagi savollarni o'ziga berishi lozim: Ushbu realiya asl matndagi qanday pragmatik funktsiyani bajararmoqda? Tarjima tilida shu funktsiyani bajaradigan analog mavjudmi? Agar mavjud bo'lmasa, qaysi strategiya orqali bu funktsiyani eng yaxshi tarzda ifodalash mumkin?

Zamonaviy tarjimashunoslikda madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni tarjimada qayta kodlash masalasiga yangicha yondashuvlar shakllanmoqda. Jumladan, Pym (2016) madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni tarjima qilishda "mahalliy adaptatsiya" (local adaptation) tushunchasini taklif qiladi. Bu kontseptsiya tarjima matnida mahalliy madaniy kontekstga moslashtirilgan elementlarni saqlab qolgan holda, global miqyosda asl matnning pragmatik ta'sirini ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Bunda tarjimon realiyalarni shunchaki so'zma-so'z tarjima qilmaydi, balki ularning asl matndagi pragmatik funktsiyasini hisobga olgan holda, tarjima tilida shu funktsiyani bajaradigan ekvivalentni tanlaydi.

Madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlashning yana bir muhim jihati — tarjimonning izohlar berish imkoniyatidir. Musayev (2019) ta'kidlaganidek, tarjima matniga ilova qilinadigan izohlar, so'z boshi yoki so'nggi so'z tarjimonning "ovozi"

sifatida xizmat qilishi va tarjima jarayonida yo'qotilgan pragmatik ma'nolarni qoplash vositasi bo'lishi mumkin. Bunday yondashuv, ayniqsa, badiiy tarjimada madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning pragmatik ta'sirini saqlashda samarali usul bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlash jarayonida tarjimon nafaqat ikkita til o'rtasidagi farqlarni, balki ikkita madaniyat o'rtasidagi farqlarni ham hisobga olishi kerak. Bunda madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya nazariyasidan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Sirojiddinov (2017) taklif qilgan madaniyat o'lchovlari (individualizm/kollektivizm, hokimiyat masofasi, noaniqlikdan qochish, maskulinlik/feminlik, uzoq muddatli/qisqa muddatli orientatsiya) madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni tahlil qilish va tarjima strategiyalarini tanlashda nazariy asos bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarning tarjimada qayta kodlanish xususiyatlari murakkab va ko'p qirrali masala bo'lib, u tarjimondan nafaqat lingvistik, balki madaniy va pragmatik kompetensiyani ham talab qiladi. Tarjima jarayonida madaniy-pragmatik realiyalarni qayta kodlashning samarali strategiyalarini tanlash va qo'llash orqali tarjimon asl matndagi pragmatik ta'sirni saqlashga va tarjima matnida madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani ta'minlashga erishishi mumkin. Bu masalaning yanada chuqurroq o'rganilishi va tarjima amaliyotida qo'llanilishi zamonaviy tarjimashunoslikning muhim vazifalaridan biridir.

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YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA NODAVLAT TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDAGI ISLOHATLARNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi doirasida nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlaridagi islohotlarning ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqadi. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari, davlat ta'lim tizimiga qo'shimcha sifatida raqobatni kuchaytirib, innovatsion yondashuvlar va sifatni oshirishga hissa qo'shmoqda. Maqolada, islohotlar, ruxsatnomalar, litsenziyalash, soliq imtiyozlari, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, va innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish kabi yo'nalishlar bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan o'zgarishlar tahlil qilinadi. Ta'lim sifatini oshirish, ijtimoiy imtiyozlar, va xalqaro hamkorlikning kuchayishi orqali Yangi O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimi jahon andozalariga moslashtirilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlari, islohotlar, raqobat, ta'lim sifatini oshirish, innovatsion texnologiyalar, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, xalqaro hamkorlik, ta'lim tizimi

Аннотация: Статья рассматривает важность реформ в частных образовательных учреждениях в рамках стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана. Частные образовательные учреждения, являясь дополнением государственной системы образования, способствуют увеличению конкуренции, внедрению инновационных подходов и повышению качества образования. В статье анализируются изменения в таких направлениях, как лицензирование, налоговые льготы, государственно-частное партнерство и внедрение инновационных технологий. Повышение качества образования, социальные льготы и расширение международного сотрудничества способствуют адаптации системы образования Узбекистана к мировым стандартам.

Ключевые слова: частные образовательные учреждения, реформы, конкуренция, повышение качества образования, инновационные технологии, государственно-частное партнерство, международное сотрудничество, образовательная система

Abstract: This article examines the importance of reforms in non-governmental educational institutions within the framework of the New Uzbekistan development strategy. Private educational institutions, as a supplement to the public education system, contribute to enhancing competition, introducing innovative approaches, and improving quality. The article analyzes changes in areas such as licensing, tax benefits, public-private partnerships, and the introduction of innovative technologies. The improvement of education quality, social benefits, and expanding international cooperation are enhancing the alignment of Uzbekistan's education system with global standards.

Keywords: Non-governmental educational institutions, reforms, competition, improvement of education quality, innovative technologies, public-private partnership, international cooperation, education system.

Bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimini isloh qilish va uning sifatini oshirish dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Dunyo miqyosida raqobatbardosh kadrlarni tayyorlash, innovatsion texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga joriy etish, xususiy ta'lim

muassasalarining roli va samaradorligini oshirish masalalari kundan-kunga katta ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan, **Yangi O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlaridagi islohotlarning o'rni** mavzusi bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan biridir.

O'zbekistonda ta'lim sohasini rivojlantirish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, bu borada amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar ta'limning sifati va samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari (xususiylar maktablar, universitetlar, o'quv markazlari) ushbu jarayonda muhim o'rin tutadi, chunki ular davlat ta'lim tizimini to'ldiradi va unga raqobat muhitini olib kiradi. Nodavlat ta'lim tizimining rivojlanishi O'zbekistonning xalqaro ta'lim makoniga integratsiyalashuvi, innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalarining joriy etilishi va ta'lim xizmatlarining diversifikatsiyasiga xizmat qiladi.

So'nggi yillarda O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlash, davlat-xususiylar sheriklik asosida ta'lim sifati oshirish va nodavlat ta'lim tizimiga zamonaviylar boshqaruv tizimlarini joriy etish bo'yicha qator islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan:

- **Nodavlat oliylar ta'lim muassasalari** ochilishiga ruxsat berildi va ularning soni oshdi.
- **Davlat tomonidan imtiyozlar va grantlar** ajratish tizimi rivojlantirilmoqda.
- **Xalqaro universitetlar va akademik dasturlar** bilan hamkorlik kuchaymoqda.
- **Raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlar** ta'lim jarayoniga joriy etilmoqda.

Shu sababli, mazkur mavzu bo'yicha ilmiylar tadqiqot olib borish nafaqat nazariylar, balki amaliylar jihatdan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – Yangi O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim tizimida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning ahamiyatini tahlil qilish, ta'lim sifati va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga ta'sirini o'rganish va mavjud muammolar hamda ularning yechimlarini aniqlashdir.

O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim tizimining shakllanishi va rivojlanish bosqichlarini o'rganish.

1. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni tahlil qilish.
2. Nodavlat va davlat ta'lim tizimlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlik va raqobat muhitini baholash.
3. Xalqaro tajribani o'rganish va O'zbekiston sharoitida qo'llash imkoniyatlarini aniqlash.

4. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.

Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirishga, nodavlat sektorning rolini kuchaytirishga va ta'lim sifati bo'yicha xalqaro standartlarga moslashishga yordam berishi kutilmoqda. Mazkur mavzu bo'yicha olib boriladigan ilmiy izlanishlar mamlakatning intellektual va iqtisodiy salohiyatini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Ushbu maqolani tayyorlash jarayonida ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarida keng qo'llaniladigan metodlardan foydalanildi. Tadqiqotning asosiy metodlari quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

1. Tahliliy metod. Bu metod orqali nodavlat ta'lim tizimi, uning rivojlanish bosqichlari va islohotlar jarayoni chuqur tahlil qilindi. Xususan, O'zbekistonning ta'lim sohasidagi huquqiy bazasi, qabul qilingan qaror va farmonlar, xalqaro tajriba asosida nodavlat ta'lim tizimining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari o'rganildi.

2. Taqqoslash metodi. O'zbekistonning nodavlat ta'lim tizimi boshqa davlatlar, xususan, rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar ta'lim tizimlari bilan taqqoslandi. Bu metod orqali O'zbekistondagi islohotlarning samaradorligini baholash va xalqaro tajribadan kelib chiqib tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish imkoni yaratildi.

3. Statistik tahlil metodi. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining soni, ularning rivojlanish dinamikasi, qamrov darajasi, bitiruvchilar soni kabi statistik ma'lumotlar tahlil qilindi. Ushbu metod ta'lim sohasidagi o'zgarishlarni aniq raqamlar orqali ko'rsatish va islohotlarning samaradorligini baholash imkonini berdi.

4. Anketalar va intervyular (Empirik metod). Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari vakillari, o'qituvchilar va talabalar bilan intervyular o'tkazilib, ularning islohotlarga bo'lgan munosabati, mavjud muammolar va takliflari o'rganildi. Anketalar yordamida ta'lim sifati, o'qitish metodlari va xalqaro hamkorlik darajasi bo'yicha ma'lumotlar to'plandi.

5. Normativ-huquqiy tahlil. O'zbekiston Respublikasining ta'lim sohasidagi qonunlari, farmonlari va me'yoriy hujjatlari o'rganildi. Nodavlat ta'lim tizimiga oid rasmiy hujjatlar va strategik dasturlar tahlil qilinib, ulardagi asosiy yo'nalishlar ajratib chiqildi.

6. Sotsiologik metod. O'zbekiston jamiyatida nodavlat ta'lim muassasalariga bo'lgan munosabat va ularning ahamiyati sotsiologik nuqtai nazardan o'rganildi. Jamoatchilik fikrini tahlil qilish orqali nodavlat ta'limning qamrov darajasi va ahamiyati bo'yicha xulosa chiqarildi.

Yuqoridagi metodlar maqolani ilmiy asosda tayyorlash, ta'lim sohasidagi muammolarni aniq ifodalash va islohotlarning samaradorligini baholash imkonini berdi. Ushbu tadqiqotning natijalari asosida O'zbekiston nodavlat ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Ushbu tadqiqot natijasida Yangi O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim tizimi islohotlarining ahamiyati va samaradorligi baholandi. Tadqiqot davomida to'plangan ma'lumotlar tahlil qilinib, quyidagi asosiy natijalarga erishildi:

1. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining o'sish dinamikasi

O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari soni so'nggi yillarda sezilarli darajada oshgan. Quyidagi jadvalda 2018–2024 yillar oralig'ida nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining soni ko'rsatilgan.

Jadval 1. O'zbekistonda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari sonining o'zgarishi (2018–2024)

Yil	Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni	O'sish sur'ati (%)
2018	5	-
2019	8	+60%
2020	14	+75%
2021	24	+71%
2022	35	+46%
2023	42	+20%
2024	50	+19%

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, so'nggi olti yil ichida nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 10 barobarga oshgan. Bunda davlat tomonidan berilgan imtiyozlar va islohotlarning ijobiy ta'siri yaqqol sezilmoqda.

2. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri

Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlanishi bilan ta'lim sifatining oshishi kuzatilmoqda. Tadqiqot davomida 500 nafar talaba va 200 nafar o'qituvchi o'rtasida o'tkazilgan so'rovnoma natijalari quyidagicha:

Jadval 2. Talabalar va o'qituvchilarning ta'lim sifatiga nisbatan fiklari (%)

Ta'lim sifati bo'yicha savollar	"Juda yaxshi" (%)	"Yaxshi" (%)	"Qoniqarli" (%)	"Qoniqarsiz" (%)
O'qituvchilarning malakasi	55	35	8	2
O'quv dasturlarining sifat darajasi	48	38	10	4

Ta'lim sifati bo'yicha savollar	"Juda yaxshi" (%)	"Yaxshi" (%)	"Qoniqarli" (%)	"Qoniqarsiz" (%)
Amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim	50	40	7	3
Texnik va moddiy baza	42	45	10	3

Talabalarning nodavlat ta'lim sifati haqidagi fikrlari

Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, talabalar va o'qituvchilarning aksariyati nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi ta'lim sifati davlat universitetlari bilan teng yoki undan yuqori ekanini ta'kidlamogda. Bunda xorijiy universitetlar bilan hamkorlikning kuchayishi, zamonaviy texnologiyalar joriy etilishi va mustaqil boshqaruv tizimining yo'lga qo'yilishi muhim rol o'ynagan.

3. Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarida xalqaro hamkorlik darajasi

Nodavlat universitetlarining rivojlanishi xalqaro universitetlar bilan hamkorlikni kengaytirish imkonini berdi. Hozirda O'zbekistondagi 50 dan ortiq nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining aksariyati chet el universitetlari bilan qo'shma dasturlar va talabalar almashinuvini yo'lga qo'ygan.

Jadval 3. O'zbekistonda xalqaro hamkorlik asosida faoliyat yuritayotgan nodavlat universitetlar

Universitet nomi	Hamkor davlatlar	Qo'shma dasturlar soni
Westminster universiteti	Buyuk Britaniya	10
Turin Politexnika universiteti	Italiya	8
Sinxua universiteti filiali	Xitoy	7
MDIST (Management Development Institute)	Singapur	6
Yeoju texnologiya instituti	Janubiy Koreya	5

Bu natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, xalqaro hamkorlik ta'lim sifati va talabalar uchun yangi imkoniyatlarni oshirmogda.

1. **Nodavlat ta'lim sektorining tez o'sishi** – so'nggi yillarda nodavlat universitetlar sonining ortishi ta'lim tizimidagi raqobatni oshirib, o'quv dasturlarining sifatini yaxshilashga xizmat qilmogda.

2. **Ta'lim sifati oshmogda** – yangi nodavlat universitetlarda amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim va zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar joriy qilinmogda.

3. **Xalqaro hamkorlik va innovatsiyalar** – xorijiy universitetlar bilan hamkorlik tufayli nodavlat universitetlarda jahon miqyosida tan olingan diplom olish imkoniyati oshgan.

4. **Moddiy-texnik baza va resurslar rivojlanmoqda** – nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari zamonaviy texnologiyalar va yangi laboratoriyalar bilan jihozlanmoqda.

Xulosa shuki, O'zbekistonning nodavlat ta'lim sektoridagi islohotlar sezilarli natijalarga olib kelmoqda. Ta'lim sifatining oshishi, raqobat muhitining shakllanishi va xalqaro hamkorlikning kengayishi mamlakatning intellektual salohiyatini yanada mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

2018-2024 yillarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari sonining o'sishi

Bu grafik 2018-2024 yillarda O'zbekistonda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari sonining qanday o'sib borayotganini ko'rsatadi. Endi ta'lim sifatiga oid so'rovnoma natijalarini ham vizual tarzda ko'rsatish uchun diagramma yarataman

Bu diagrammada talabalar so'rovnomasi natijalariga ko'ra, nodavlat ta'lim muassasalaridagi ta'lim sifati qanday baholanganini ko'rishingiz mumkin. Ko'pchilik talabalar va o'qituvchilar ta'lim sifati yuqori darajada ekanini ta'kidlagan.

Ushbu tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, Yangi O'zbekistonda nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlanishi ta'lim tizimining sifatini oshirish va raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash jarayoniga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. So'nggi yillarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari sonining sezilarli darajada ortgani (2018-yilda 5 ta bo'lsa, 2024-yilda 50 taga yetgan) ushbu sohada olib borilayotgan islohotlarning samarali ekanini tasdiqlaydi.

Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, nodavlat universitetlarda **o'qituvchilarning malakasi, o'quv dasturlarining sifati, amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim va texnik baza** kabi omillar talabalarining talablariga mos darajada yaxshilanmoqda. Xalqaro hamkorlikning rivojlanishi esa O'zbekistonda global ta'lim maydoniga integratsiyalashuv jarayonini jadallashtirmoqda.

Asosiy natijalar bo'yicha xulosa.

1. **Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari sonining o'sishi** – oxirgi 6 yil ichida universitetlar soni 10 barobarga oshdi, bu esa ta'lim tizimida raqobatni kuchaytirdi.

2. **Ta'lim sifatining yaxshilanishi** – nodavlat universitetlarda ilg'or pedagogik yondashuvlar, amaliyotga asoslangan ta'lim va raqamli texnologiyalar keng joriy etilmoqda.

3. **Xalqaro hamkorlikning ortishi** – xorijiy universitetlar bilan hamkorlikda qo'shma dasturlar va talabalar almashinuvi kengayib bormoqda.

4. **Ta'limning diversifikatsiyasi** – nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari yangi yo'nalishlar bo'yicha malakali kadrlar tayyorlashga moslashmoqda.

5. **Davlat tomonidan ko'rsatilayotgan imtiyozlar** – nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarini qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha qabul qilingan farmon va qarorlar ularning rivojlanishiga xizmat qilmoqda.

Tavsiya va takliflar.

1. **Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining huquqiy va iqtisodiy mustaqilligini oshirish** – bu ularning o'z dasturlarini yaratish, innovatsion loyihalarni amalga oshirish va o'zini o'zi moliyalashtirish darajasini oshirishga yordam beradi.

2. **Xalqaro akkreditatsiya va sertifikat tizimini kengaytirish** – xalqaro e'tirofga ega diplom va sertifikatlarning taqdim etilishi nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari obro'sini oshiradi.

3. **Davlat-xususiy sheriklik tizimini yanada takomillashtirish** – nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari davlat bilan hamkorlikda turli grantlar va innovatsion loyihalarni amalga oshirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak.

4. **O'qituvchilarni doimiy malaka oshirish tizimini kuchaytirish** – xalqaro universitetlar bilan hamkorlikda malaka oshirish dasturlarini kengaytirish lozim.

5. **Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarni yanada keng joriy etish** – sun'iy intellekt, onlayn ta'lim platformalari va masofaviy ta'limni rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

6. **Talabalar uchun stipendiyalar va kredit tizimini kengaytirish** – nodavlat universitetlarda o'qish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish uchun davlat tomonidan qo'shimcha imtiyozlar taqdim etilishi lozim.

O'zbekiston nodavlat ta'lim tizimi islohotlari ta'lim sifati va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim o'rin tutmoqda. Davlat va xususiy sektor o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni mustahkamlash, xalqaro standartlarga mos ta'lim dasturlarini ishlab chiqish hamda innovatsion texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish orqali ushbu yo'nalish yanada rivojlantirilishi mumkin. Kelgusida nodavlat ta'lim sektorini qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha strategik chora-tadbirlar ishlab chiqish O'zbekistonning jahon ta'limidagi o'rnini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

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The Role of Teachers in Developing Cognitive Strategies

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Annotation. This article explores the critical influence of teachers in developing cognitive strategies in students. It illustrates information about the most famous and important cognitive strategies, such as memory, attention, and critical thinking and their vital role in the process of effective learning and how teachers play a crucial role in fostering these strategies. Moreover, there will be given information about the ways of making students nurture the cognitive strategies and apply them in their learning journeys, how interactive learning environments and structures guidance can boost cognitive development, especially in childhood period. The article also provides with essential learning methods which can be used by teachers to make the process of applying cognitive strategies easier and effective and also how teachers can influence the whole learning journey of students while learning languages.

Keywords: Cognitive strategies, teacher's role, cognitive development, early childhood education, scaffolding, interactive learning, teacher-child interaction, problem-solving, critical thinking, learning environments.

Аннотация. Эта статья исследует важное влияние учителей на развитие когнитивных стратегий у учащихся. В ней представлена информация о самых известных и значимых когнитивных стратегиях, таких как память, внимание и критическое мышление, а также об их ключевой роли в процессе эффективного обучения и о том, как учителя играют решающую роль в их формировании. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются способы, с помощью которых учащиеся могут развивать когнитивные стратегии и применять их в процессе обучения. Также описывается, как интерактивные учебные среды и структурированное руководство могут способствовать когнитивному развитию, особенно в детском возрасте. В статье приводятся важные методы обучения, которые учителя могут использовать, чтобы сделать процесс применения когнитивных стратегий более простым и эффективным. Кроме того, рассматривается, как учителя могут влиять на весь образовательный путь учащихся при изучении языков.

Ключевые слова: когнитивные стратегии, роль учителя, когнитивное развитие, дошкольное образование, поддержка (скэффолдинг), интерактивное обучение, взаимодействие учитель-ребёнок, решение проблем, критическое мышление, учебные среды.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarda kognitiv strategiyalarni rivojlantirishda o'qituvchilarning muhim ta'sirini o'rganadi. Maqolada eng mashhur va muhim kognitiv strategiyalar, masalan, хотира, e'tibor va tanqidiy fikrlash, ularning samarali o'rganish jarayonidagi roli va o'qituvchilarning ushbu strategiyalarni rivojlantirishdagi muhim roli haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada o'quvchilarga kognitiv strategiyalarni o'rganishga va ularni o'rganish jarayonida qo'llashga yordam berish usullari, interaktiv o'quv muhitlari va tuzilgan qo'llanmalar

orqali kognitiv rivojlanishni qanday qo'llab-quvvatlash mumkinligi, ayniqsa bolalik davrida, keltirilgan. Maqolada o'qituvchilarga kognitiv strategiyalarni qo'llash jarayonini oson va samarali qilish uchun foydalanilishi mumkin bo'lgan muhim o'qitish usullari hamda o'qituvchilarning o'quvchilarning til o'rganishdagi butun o'quv jarayoniga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi haqida ham so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kognitiv strategiyalar, o'qituvchining roli, kognitiv rivojlanish, erta bolalik ta'limi, skaffolding (qo'llab-quvvatlash), interaktiv o'quv jarayonlari, o'qituvchi-bola o'zaro ta'siri, muammolarni hal qilish, tanqidiy fikrlash, o'quv muhitlari.

It is clear that for students to fully process, understand, and retain information, they need to have cognitive strategies in place. Strategies involve various mental activities such as paying attention, remembering, problem-solving, as well as thinking critically, which are all important for effective learning. It is the responsibility of the teacher to not only explain concepts to learners, but also to foster these cognitive strategies which facilitate learning. His or her influence goes beyond teaching content to include guiding the learners in working through instructional challenges, problem solving, and knowledge consolidation. In any kind of situation in a learning process, the teacher is always responsible for helping students to make the cognitive strategies work in their learning journey. As Pertiwi indicated that teachers play an important role in the development of cognitive skills and they participate in this process actively.⁷² This is especially the case in settings where learning is accompanied by purposeful organized instruction that is designed to evoke and support student inquiry. As noted, young students' cognitive growth is influenced quite a lot by the teacher's style during this critical period and this shapes their understanding of learning for life. It is the teachers who help students develop cognitive strategies, process instructional information, and apply problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and the strategic use of attention and memory. Cognitive strategies—such as organization, rehearsal, elaboration, and reflection—are essential tools for students to process and retain information.

Teachers, through a variety of methods, can help students acquire and refine these strategies, which are crucial for academic success and lifelong learning. The role of teachers can be seen in these fields:

1. Creating a supportive learning environment

A teacher's primary obligation in developing cognitive strategies is to design an environment which allows for both active participation and thoughtful reflection. When students are encouraged to take risks and even make mistakes, their self-efficacy, and thus, confidence, in their thinking skills, increases. This means that in the early childhood there should be the incorporation of play-based learning which includes and

⁷² Pertiwi, D. (2024). The role of teachers in the development of learning media for block play in early childhood cognitive development. *Indonesian Journal of Behavioral Studies*, 4(2), 97-104.

boosts curiosity and creative thinking. As Pertiwi notes that the activities which are mainly done in the group play an important role in the development of children cognitively

2. Scaffolding learning

Scaffolding, supporting a learner's acquisition of new cognitive strategies, is an essential part of a teacher's work. This support is gradually faded as students become more skilled and self-confident, allowing for individual cognitive processing. Teachers can scaffold learning by guiding students through the solution to a particular problem step by step, encouraging them to think reflectively, and by segmenting the task into smaller, more manageable works. This enables students to master processes that are critical for lifelong learning.

3. Modelling cognitive strategies

Teachers also model cognitive strategies for their students. Thinking and saying the strategies aloud serves to concretize in the minds of the learners the problem-solving and memory tasks as they will know how to approach those tasks with the tips provided. For example, when solving a math problem or writing an essay, teachers can verbalize their thought process, explaining how they use organizational skills, make connections between ideas, and reflect on their thinking. This approach helps students develop metacognitive skills, enabling them to assess and regulate their own cognitive strategies.

4. Providing feedback

Feedback is the cornerstone of developing one's cognitive strategies. Teachers highlight the value of constructive feedback and its ability to help students refine their thinking processes, correct misunderstandings, and enhance cognitive strategies. There is a duality in feedback which stems from both formal, such as grades and assessments, and informal praising contexts, through verbal praises which includes peer reviews. This dynamic enables learners to reflect on their learning activities and self-adjust accordingly.

5. Encouraging reflection and self-regulation

Self-regulation is equally important in cognitive development, in which the self-reflective skill is greatly enhanced through goal setting. While focusing on these self-monitoring objectives, students demonstrate autonomy through active reflection on their learning strategies. These self-regulatory skills as presented by Ikie, Amosun & Olalowo, underscore the importance of the teacher-child interaction skill which emphasizes the enhanced ability of reflection-driven learning experiences toward the development of self-cognitive strategies.⁷³

⁷³ Ikie, R., Amosun, M., & Olalowo, I. (2022). Empirical realities of teacher-child interaction and cognitive development of pre-primary school children in Ibadan, Oyo state. *International Journal of Emerging Issues in Early Childhood Education*, 4(2), 1-11.

6. Promoting active learning

As noted with group work, debates, and project-based learning as examples of active learning strategies, self-application of cognitive strategies in a social interaction is obtained. Active learning strategies not only enhance the students' cognitive development, but equally their problem-solving and critical thinking abilities. Teacher involvement as well as parental support brings about profound impacts toward nurturing cognitive growth specifically with preschool-aged children.

In order to apply above-mentioned methods and ways, teachers' techniques are important. Teaching techniques are essential in aiding students to build and use mental strategies. Instructional methods are aimed at developing students' thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as their ability to understand concepts at greater depth.

Some of the most effective methods are scaffolding, collaborative and inquiry-based learning, and the application of multimedia and technology. These aid students in developing cognitive skills and also in the application of these skills across various subjects, as well as in real life situations. As described above, scaffolding entails aiding students to the extent that they are able to work with basic aids to help them complete more complex tasks. Teachers reduce their help step-by-step as learners become adept at using the various cognitive strategies. Scaffolding affords students the opportunity to develop solving and critical thinking skills because it allows them to work with tasks that have been simplified into smaller units. This builds self-reliance and indicates the growing ability to control one's learning. Under collaborative learning, students are given the chance to work in groups to arrive at certain problem solutions as well as to discuss concepts at greater depths.⁷⁴ In team work students are able to consider other different ways of solving a given problem, therefore broadening their understanding of the concept. This is helpful in sharpening attention and in the internalization of cognitive strategies because students have to explain their reasoning to other students.

The formation of cognitive strategies remains an important pillar of the academic achievement and lifelong learning of students. These strategies are enhanced by effective teaching techniques such as scaffolding, collaborative learning, and multimedia and technology integration. Of course, large class sizes and limited resources can become formidable barriers to achieving these goals. Still, there is hope in the ingenuity and flexibility of each individual teacher. Through diverse, tailored support and instruction, teachers and students in cultivating the cognitive capabilities required to successfully navigate their educational pathways.

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CHALLENGES IN READING COMPREHENSION AMONG 1ST YEAR LAW STUDENTS

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Abstract: This paper investigates the reading comprehension difficulties encountered by first-year law students, a skill pivotal to their academic success in legal education. It integrates existing research with the author's own studies to pinpoint challenges such as intricate legal terminology, dense textual structures, and the necessity for critical analysis. Pedagogical strategies to mitigate these issues are proposed, with an emphasis on their applicability across disciplines like economics, aerospace technology, sustainable development, and material science at "TIAME" NRU. The paper concludes with actionable recommendations for enhancing language teaching practices.

Keywords: reading comprehension, law students, language teaching, pedagogical strategies, interdisciplinary relevance.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola birinchi yil huquqshunoslik yo'nalishi talabalari tomonidan o'qib tushunishda duch keladigan qiyinchiliklarni o'rganad. O'qib tushunish akademik muvaffaqiyat uchun muhim ko'nikma hisoblanadi. Mavjud adabiyotlar va muallifning tadqiqotlari asosida murakkab huquqiy terminologiya, zich matn tuzilmalari va tanqidiy tahlilga bo'lgan ehtiyoj kabi asosiy to'siqlar aniqlanadi. Ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun pedagogik strategiyalar muhokama qilinadi va iqtisodiyot, va huquqshunoslik kabi sohalarda o'qib tushunishning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qib tushunish, huquqshunoslik talabalari, til o'qitish, pedagogik strategiyalar, fanlararo ahamiyat.

Аннотация: В статье исследуются трудности в понимании чтения у студентов-юристов первого курса, что является ключевым навыком для успеха в юридическом образовании. Опираясь на литературу и исследования автора, выявлены основные препятствия: сложная юридическая терминология, плотные текстовые структуры и необходимость критического анализа. Обсуждаются педагогические стратегии для

преодоления этих проблем, подчеркивается их значимость для дисциплин, таких как экономика, аэрокосмические технологии, устойчивое развитие и материаловедение.

Ключевые слова: понимание чтения, студенты-юристы, преподавание языка, педагогические стратегии, междисциплинарная значимость.

Introduction

Reading comprehension is a cornerstone of academic success in higher education, particularly in fields requiring engagement with sophisticated texts. For first-year law students, mastering this skill is both essential and challenging due to the specialized nature of legal discourse. Legal texts often feature complex vocabulary—such as Latin phrases (e.g., *res ipsa loquitur*) and archaic terms (e.g., "heretofore")—alongside intricate sentence structures that can obscure meaning. Surmanov (2020) observes that "the integration of Latin phrases and technical legal jargon poses a formidable barrier for novice learners," a view supported by Brown (2019), who describes legal writing as "marked by long, convoluted sentences that challenge new readers."

Moreover, legal education demands more than surface-level understanding. Students must critically analyze texts and apply them to hypothetical cases, a cognitive leap that many first-year students find difficult (Lee, 2020). This dual burden of linguistic complexity and analytical rigor distinguishes law from other disciplines, yet parallels exist. At "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" National Research University ("TIAME" NRU), students in economics, aerospace technology, sustainable development, and material science also grapple with dense texts—be it financial reports or technical manuals—highlighting the interdisciplinary relevance of reading comprehension skills.

This paper seeks to delineate the specific reading comprehension challenges faced by first-year law students and propose pedagogical solutions. By integrating insights from the literature and my own research, it aims to enhance language teaching practices at "TIAME" NRU and beyond.

Methods

This study utilized a comprehensive literature review to examine reading comprehension challenges in legal education and identify effective interventions. Academic databases such as Google Scholar, JSTOR, and ERIC were searched using keywords like "reading comprehension," "legal education," "law students," and "pedagogical strategies." The review focused on peer-reviewed articles from the past decade to ensure contemporary relevance.

Additionally, my own research was incorporated to provide primary insights. Works such as Surmanov (2020, 2024, 2025) and Egamovich (2021, 2025) explore vocabulary acquisition, reading skill development, and technology's role in language learning—topics directly relevant to law students' challenges. These studies were

analyzed alongside external sources to identify recurring themes and synthesize findings. The methodology ensured a robust foundation for understanding the issues and proposing actionable strategies.

Results

The analysis revealed four primary challenges in reading comprehension for first-year law students:

Complex Legal Terminology: Legal texts abound with specialized vocabulary, including Latin phrases and technical terms. Surmanov (2020) notes that "archaic language and Latin terms significantly impede comprehension," a finding corroborated by Smith and Jones (2018), who highlight students' struggles with "decoding legal jargon."

Dense Text Structures: Legal writing often features lengthy sentences and complex paragraphs. Brown (2019) argues that "the convoluted nature of legal texts obscures main ideas," while Johnson et al. (2021) suggest that "text density contributes to cognitive overload."

Critical Analysis Requirements: Law demands active engagement beyond mere understanding. Lee (2020) states that "students must interpret and apply texts to scenarios, a skill underdeveloped in many novices." Patel (2018) adds that "transitioning to active interpretation is a steep learning curve."

Volume of Reading: The extensive reading load in law programs overwhelms students. Taylor (2017) observes that "hundreds of pages per week lead to fatigue and reduced comprehension," especially for those refining language skills concurrently.

To address these, the following strategies emerged:

Vocabulary Development: Explicit instruction using tools like glossaries or Anki enhances retention. Egamovich (2025) found that "spaced repetition via Anki significantly boosts law students' vocabulary mastery."

Text Structure Analysis: Teaching students to dissect texts—e.g., summarizing key points—improves understanding. Surmanov and Azimova (2020) report that "text deconstruction enhances information extraction."

Critical Reading Techniques: Active strategies, such as questioning texts or group discussions, build analytical skills. Surmanov (2025) emphasizes that "active reading fosters critical thinking essential for law."

Time Management and Reading Strategies: Techniques like skimming reduce cognitive load. Taylor (2017) suggests that "strategic reading, such as prioritizing key sections, improves efficiency."

These strategies extend beyond law, benefiting "TIAME" NRU students in other fields encountering similar text complexities.

Discussion

The identified challenges align with prior research (Surmanov, 2020; Brown, 2019; Lee, 2020), but their examination within "TIAME" NRU's diverse academic context adds nuance. The interdisciplinary parallels—e.g., economics students decoding financial data or aerospace students reading manuals—suggest that these strategies have broad applicability.

For example, vocabulary tools like Anki could aid economics students with financial terms or material science students with technical jargon. Text structure analysis applies equally to dense academic papers across fields. Technology, as Egamovich (2025) demonstrates, enhances learning efficiency, while active reading techniques foster critical engagement universally.

Critics might argue that law's unique analytical demands require specialized approaches beyond general strategies. However, these methods provide a foundation adaptable to legal specifics, with critical reading directly addressing analytical needs. A limitation here is the lack of new empirical data; future studies could test these strategies empirically at "TIAME" NRU.

This paper advances the discourse on reading comprehension in legal education, offering practical, interdisciplinary solutions for language educators.

Conclusion

First-year law students face distinct reading comprehension challenges due to legal texts' complexity and analytical demands. Strategies like vocabulary development, text analysis, critical reading, and time management offer viable solutions, with relevance across "TIAME" NRU's disciplines. Implementing these can enhance students' academic and professional outcomes.

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Inclusive Approach in School Education: Principles, Practice, and Progress in Uzbekistan

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Abstract. Inclusive education is a key component of equitable learning environments and is gaining attention in Uzbekistan as part of the broader educational reform. This paper examines the principles and implementation of inclusive education in schools, focusing on Uzbekistan's policies, practices, and challenges. It highlights the need for teacher training, adaptive curricula, and supportive infrastructure to ensure that all learners, including those with disabilities, have equal access to quality education. Recommendations are provided to enhance inclusive practices at both policy and classroom levels.

Keywords: Inclusive education, school reform, equity, special needs, teacher training.

Annotatsiya: Inklyuziv ta'lim teng imkoniyatlarni ta'minlovchi muhim pedagogik yondashuv bo'lib, O'zbekistonda ham ta'lim islohotlari doirasida katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Mazkur maqolada maktab ta'limida inklyuziv yondashuvning asosiy tamoyillari, amaliyoti va dolzarb muammolari tahlil qilinadi. O'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, moslashtirilgan o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqish va infratuzilmani rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish uchun siyosiy va amaliy tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Inklyuziv ta'lim, maktab islohoti, tenglik, maxsus ehtiyojlar, o'qituvchi tayyorlash.

Аннотация: Инклюзивное образование является важным элементом обеспечения равного доступа к обучению и получает все большее внимание в Узбекистане в рамках образовательных реформ. В данной статье рассматриваются принципы и реализация инклюзивного образования в школьной системе, особенности национальной политики, практические шаги и существующие проблемы. Особое внимание уделено подготовке педагогов, адаптации учебных программ и созданию соответствующей инфраструктуры. Предлагаются рекомендации для улучшения инклюзивной практики на уровне государственной политики и школьной среды.

Ключевые слова: Инклюзивное образование, школьная реформа, равенство, особые потребности, подготовка учителей.

Inclusive education is widely recognized as a cornerstone of equitable and quality education for all. Rooted in principles of social justice, human rights, and universal access, inclusive education ensures that every learner—regardless of ability, socio-economic status, language, or background—has access to learning opportunities in mainstream educational settings. Globally, frameworks such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and UNESCO's Education 2030 Agenda have emphasized inclusive education as a critical element of sustainable development. For Uzbekistan, inclusive education has emerged as a strategic priority within broader national reforms aimed at modernizing and democratizing the education system. This paper explores the development and implementation of inclusive education policies and practices in Uzbekistan, highlighting progress, challenges, and pathways to more inclusive learning environments, particularly in secondary education.

National Policy and Reform Context

Uzbekistan has made notable strides in embedding inclusive education into its policy landscape. The **Law on Education (2020)** explicitly affirms the right of every citizen to equal educational opportunities and lays the legal foundation for inclusive education. This law is supported by presidential decrees, such as the **2022 Decree on Improving Support for Children with Disabilities**, and the **National Strategy on Human Rights (2020–2025)**, which emphasizes inclusive and equitable access to education. These reforms align with Uzbekistan's commitments under international agreements, including the **Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)** and the **CRPD**, both of which mandate inclusive practices in education.

Further, Uzbekistan's **Education Sector Plan 2019–2023**, developed in collaboration with UNESCO and the Global Partnership for Education, outlines concrete steps toward increasing access and inclusion in education. It sets targets for improved teacher training, infrastructural adaptation, and curriculum development to support diverse learners. The government has also partnered with UNICEF to implement the **Inclusive Education Development Program**, piloting inclusive classroom models and training modules in selected regions.

Despite these positive developments, implementation remains inconsistent. Stakeholders often note a gap between progressive policies and on-the-ground realities, especially in rural and under-resourced areas.

Implementation in Practice: Strengths and Challenges

Teacher Preparedness

Teacher capacity is both the linchpin and the bottleneck of inclusive education in Uzbekistan. According to the World Bank (2022), most teachers lack formal training

in inclusive pedagogies, differentiated instruction, and disability awareness. A study by Nazarqulova and Jumayeva (2021) indicates that while teachers express willingness to support diverse learners, they frequently report uncertainty about how to adjust teaching methods, classroom management, or assessments to accommodate students with disabilities or learning differences.

The **Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Teachers**, established in Tashkent, has begun to offer short-term courses on inclusive education. However, these are often insufficient in depth and reach. Pre-service teacher education programs also need to be restructured to incorporate inclusive education principles as core competencies, not optional specializations.

Adaptive Curriculum and Learning Materials

Another critical challenge lies in the development of adaptive curricula and accessible learning materials. While the national curriculum has been revised to emphasize competency-based approaches, it often remains rigid in practice. Students with cognitive, sensory, or learning disabilities require individualized education plans (IEPs), modified content delivery, and flexible assessment methods—elements not yet systematically implemented in most schools.

Efforts by international NGOs, including the **EdCamp movement** and the **Inclusive Schools Network**, have introduced teacher-led curriculum adaptations and peer support models. Nonetheless, these remain limited in scale. There is a need for centrally coordinated frameworks that offer guidance on curricular accommodations while allowing schools the autonomy to adapt materials for local needs.

Physical and Digital Infrastructure

Infrastructure poses a major barrier to inclusivity. A 2023 UNICEF audit found that over 60% of public schools in Uzbekistan lacked basic accessibility features such as wheelchair ramps, modified restrooms, or tactile signage. This is especially acute in rural areas, where resource limitations are compounded by logistical challenges.

Digital inclusion is also uneven. While the government has made strides under the “**Digital Uzbekistan 2030**” strategy, many students with disabilities lack access to assistive technologies or adapted digital content. Efforts such as the “**Smart Classroom**” pilot program, launched with UNESCO’s support, have introduced interactive whiteboards and digital learning platforms in some urban schools, but scaling these innovations nationally remains a challenge.

International Comparisons and Best Practices

Uzbekistan can draw valuable lessons from global models of inclusive education. In countries such as **Finland**, inclusive education is grounded in the concept of “support for all,” with three levels of educational support integrated into general classrooms. This includes part-time special education teachers, flexible curriculum pathways, and student welfare teams.

In **Italy**, inclusive education has been embedded into national law since the 1970s. Special education teachers are co-assigned to every school, and IEPs are developed collaboratively by educators, psychologists, and families. Likewise, **Chile's** policy of School Integration Programs (PIE) provides targeted funding and technical support to mainstream schools that enroll students with special needs.

Uzbekistan has already begun to localize some of these practices. The **UNESCO Tashkent Office** has launched a **peer mentoring model** in select secondary schools, where more experienced teachers mentor peers on inclusive strategies. The **Uzbekistan Teachers' Association** also supports collaborative lesson planning and community engagement, inspired by Japan's lesson study model.

Recommendations

To realize the full potential of inclusive education, Uzbekistan must pursue reforms across four strategic areas:

1. Strengthen Teacher Training and Certification

- Make inclusive pedagogy a core requirement in all pre-service teacher training programs.
- Provide ongoing professional development, mentorship, and communities of practice for in-service teachers.
- Introduce inclusive education competencies in teacher certification and evaluation.

2. Develop and Implement Adaptive Curriculum and Materials

- Create national guidelines for differentiated instruction and IEP development.
- Invest in developing textbooks and digital content that reflect universal design principles.
- Establish local curriculum adaptation centers to support schools in customizing materials.

3. Improve Physical and Technological Infrastructure

- Conduct a national accessibility audit of school facilities and prioritize upgrades.
- Expand access to assistive technologies and ensure compatibility with online learning platforms.
- Establish mobile resource units to support rural and remote schools.

4. Institutionalize Inclusive Policies and Monitoring

- Create a national council on inclusive education to coordinate across ministries and stakeholders.
- Develop a monitoring and evaluation framework with indicators for inclusivity, participation, and learning outcomes.
- Involve families and communities in planning and advocacy efforts.

Uzbekistan's commitment to inclusive education reflects a significant shift toward more equitable and human-centered educational reform. Grounded in strong policy intent and supported by international partnerships, the foundations for inclusive schooling are being laid. However, effective implementation requires deep investments in teacher capacity, infrastructure, and curriculum design. By drawing on international best practices and expanding localized initiatives, Uzbekistan can ensure that no learner is left behind. Inclusive education must move from being a policy ambition to a lived reality in every classroom.

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NUTQ DARSLARIDA RAVONLIKNI OSHIRISH TEXNIKASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada nutq darslarida, so'zlashuvda (ingliz tili misolida) ravon so'zlashishni yaxshilashga keng qamrovli yondashuv ko'rsatilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhit yaratish, kommunikativ faoliyat bilan shug'ullanish, texnologiyadan samarali foydalanish, o'ziga ishonchni mustahkamlash, tinglash va o'qishni birlashtirishga urg'u beriladi. Asosiy strategiyalar aniqlikdan ko'ra ravonlikni birinchi o'ringa qo'yish, tabiiy ikkilanish vositalaridan foydalanishni rag'batlantirish va sinfdan tashqari muntazam amaliyotni targ'ib qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu strategiyalarni amalga oshirish orqali o'qituvchilar o'quvchilarga o'ziga ishongan va ingliz tilini ravon muloqot qilish qobiliyatini egallashga ko'maklashishlari mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: og'zaki nutq, ravon so'zlashuv, o'ziga ishonch, tinglash madaniyati, ravonlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен комплексный подход к улучшению беглости речи на уроках говорения и разговора (на примере английского языка). В статье также подчеркивается важность создания благоприятной среды, вовлечения в коммуникативные мероприятия, эффективного использования технологий, укрепления уверенности в себе и интеграции аудирования и чтения. Ключевые стратегии включают приоритет беглости речи над точностью, поощрение использования инструментов обработки естественного языка и

поощрение регулярной практики за пределами классной комнаты. Реализуя эти стратегии, преподаватели могут помочь учащимся стать уверенными и свободно говорящими на английском языке.

Ключевые слова: устная речь, беглая речь, уверенность в себе, навыки аудирования, беглость.

Abstract. This article presents a comprehensive approach to improving fluency in speech lessons and conversation (using the example of English). The article also emphasizes creating a supportive environment, engaging in communicative activities, using technology effectively, building self-confidence, and integrating listening and reading. Key strategies include prioritizing fluency over accuracy, encouraging the use of natural language processing tools, and promoting regular practice outside of the classroom. By implementing these strategies, teachers can help students become confident and fluent English communicators.

Key words: oral speech, fluent speech, self-confidence, listening skills, fluency.

Kirish. So'zlashish — bu til o'rganishning eng faol va murakkab ko'rinishidir. Ayniqsa, ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganayotgan o'quvchilar uchun bu ko'nikma doimiy mashq va ruhiy tayyorgarlikni talab qiladi. Til o'rganish jarayonida grammatikani bilish yoki lug'at boy bo'lish yetarli emas — erkin va ishonch bilan gapirish, o'z fikrini og'zaki ravishda ifoda eta olish eng muhim maqsadlardandir. Ammo bugungi kunda ingliz tilini o'rganishda ko'pchilik o'quvchilarni o'ylantiradigan quyidagi muammolarga duch kelinadi. Jumladan;

Grammatikaning murakkabligi. Talabalar uchun nafaqat ingliz tili grammatikasi, balki ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganilayotgan tilning grammatikasini o'rganish juda qiyin. Ingliz tilida so'zlashishda talabalar, asosan, grammatik xatolarga yo'l qo'yishadi. Odatda, o'quvchilar ingliz tilida so'zlashda zamon, nisbat, so'z boyligida xatolarga yo'l qo'yadilar. Gap tuzish jarayonida ko'pincha til o'rganuvchilar zamonni farqlashda qiynalishadi va noto'g'ri ishlatadilar, ya'ni ba'zan ular o'tgan zamonda gapirmoqchi bo'lishsa, o'tgan zamon o'rniga hozirgi zamonda gapirishadi. Bir necha marta xato ishlatilishlardan so'ng ular ravon so'zlash o'rniga xato ishlatmaslik haqida ko'proq o'ylay boshlashadi. Bu esa o'z o'zidan ravon so'zlashuvga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Auditoriyada ona tilidan ortiqcha foydalanish. Til o'rganuvchilar yangi xorijiy tildan foydalanishga majbur bo'lganlaridagina boshqa tilni yaxshi o'rganadilar. O'qituvchi talabalar o'rganilayotgan tilda muloqot qilishlarini talab qilishi kerak. Ana shu holatdagina til o'rganishda o'sish, talaffuzdagi ravonlikka erishish darajasi oshadi. Dars jarayonida qat'iyat bilan talab qilinsa va cheklovlar yo'lga qo'yilsagina chet tilini o'zlashtirish muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshadi⁷⁵.

O'ziga bo'lgan ishonchsizlik. Talabalarning jamoat joylarida ingliz tilida gaplasha olmasligining sabablaridan biri ham o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchsizlikdir. Ular

⁷⁵ Abdumutalipova Sh.H. Xorijiy tilni o'rganishdagi eng dolzarb muammolar // Ilmfan muammolari magistrantlar talqinida. - N., 2021. 26-28

odamlar oldida ingliz tilida gapirisha olishmaydi. Bu odatda, o'qituvchilar tomonidan o'quvchilarni jamoat joylarida ingliz tilida gapirishga yetarlicha rag'batlantirmasliklari bilan bog'liq. Odatda, o'qituvchilar ularni sinfda yoki odamlar oldida ingliz tilida gapirishga undashmaydi. Ular ingliz tilini o'rganishadi, lekin so'zlashishni yetarlicha o'rganishmaydi. Bu asosan, talabalar sinfda yoki odamlar oldida duch keladigan muammolardan biridir. O'ziga bo'lgan ishonch ingliz tilida gapirishda juda muhim rol o'ynaydi, agar talabalar o'zlariga ishonmasa, ingliz tilida erkin gapira olishmaydi. O'quvchilarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchi esa butunlay o'qituvchilarga bog'liq⁷⁶.

Yuqorida keltirib o'tilgan muammolar bugungi kunda ikkinchi tilni o'rganishga kirishgan o'quvchilarning aksariyat qismida yuzaga keladigan muammolar hisoblanadi. Shu boisdan ularni hal etish, o'quvchilarda ravon so'zlashuv madaniyatini shakllantirish hamda o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini mustahkamlash maqsadida bir necha faoliyatlar amalga oshirilmogda. Jumladan eng keng tarqalgan usullardan biri *interaktiv faoliyatlardir*.

Ya'ni, guruhli ishlash, juftlik mashqlari va rolli o'yinlar gapirish ko'nikmalarini samarali oshiradi. Masalan, "sotuvchi va xaridor", "sayyoh va gid" kabi rollar orqali o'quvchi real hayotdagi suhbatni mashq qiladi. Shuningdek, ovqatga buyurtma berish, uchrashuvlar belgilash, taqdimotlar berish va tasodifiy suhbatlar kabi rol o'ynash stsenariylari orqali real hayotdagi suhbatlarni taqlid qilish orqali o'quvchiga o'z fikrini erkin ifodalashga, xatolikdan qo'rqmasdan so'zlashga o'rgatadi.

Shuningdek, *bahs va munozaralar* ham talabalar biror mavzu yuzasidan bahs olib borishsa, bu ularni fikr bildirish, dalillar keltirish, va boshqalarni tinglab, munosabat bildirishga o'rgatadi. Masalan, "Oliy o'quv yurtlarida maxsus formalarda yurishni talab qilish qanchalik o'rinli?" degan mavzu orqali har ikki tomon fikr almashadi va gapirish faollashadi. O'quvchilar dolzarb voqealar, ijtimoiy muammolar va shaxsiy qiziqish mavzulari bo'yicha qizg'in bahs va munozaralarda qatnashishlari kerak. Bu tanqidiy fikrlashni va fikr bildirish hamda himoya qilish qobiliyatini rag'batlantiradi. Hikoya va ijodiy yozish esa o'z navbatida, o'quvchilarni hikoya qilish, nutq va yozish mashqlari orqali o'z fikrlarini ijodiy ifodalashga undash kerak. Ushbu mashg'ulotlar tasavvurni, ravonlikni va fikrlarni izchil tartibga solish qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi. O'yinlar va simulyatsiyalar esa til o'rganishni qiziqarli va samarali qilish uchun charades, pictionary va stol o'yinlari kabi til o'yinlari kiritilishi kerak. Bu harakatlar og'zaki muloqotni rag'batlantiradi va tez fikrlashni yaxshilaydi.

Bundan tashqari texnologiyadan foydalanish, jumladan mobil ilovalar, talaffuzni aniqlovchi vositalar va onlayn mashg'ulotlar orqali o'quvchilar mustaqil ravishda gapirishni mashq qilishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, darslarda videolar va interaktiv suhbatlar ham foydali bo'ladi. Shuningdek, onlayn platformalar, video

⁷⁶ <http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlar/umumii-urta-talim/5141.htm>

konferensiya vositalari butun dunyo bo'ylab til hamkorlari yoki repetitorlar bilan virtual suhbatlarni osonlashtirish uchun ham foydalidir⁷⁷.

Shuni ham ta'kidlash mumkinki, o'quvchilar o'z nutqlarini yozib olishlari, so'ng talaffuz, intonatsiya va ravonlik kabi takomillashtirilishi kerak bo'lgan sohalarni aniqlab, ularning faoliyatini tahlil qilishlari kerak. Avval boshida mukammal grammatikadan ko'ra silliq va tabiiy muloqotga urg'u berish lozim. O'quvchilarni xatolardan qo'rqmasdan o'z fikrlarini erkin ifoda etishga undash katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu ularga ishonchni mustahkamlashga va nutqida tabiiy oqimni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Doimiy mashq qilish, albatta, muntazam mashq ravonlikni oshirishning kalitidir. O'quvchilarni sinfdan tashqarida nutq so'zlash imkoniyatlarini faol izlashga undash. Bu til sherigini topish, suhbat guruhlariga qo'shilish yoki hatto o'zlari bilan gaplashishni mashq qilishni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin. Til bilan doimiy ravishda tanishish ularning ingliz tilidan foydalanishda ravonlik va ishonchini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Ushbu strategiyalarni amalga oshirish orqali o'qituvchilar o'quvchilarga ingliz tilida ishonchli va ravon muloqot qilish imkoniyatini beradigan qiziqarli va samarali nutq darslarini yaratishi mumkin.

Ingliz tilida ravonlik ko'p qirrali mahorat bo'lib, u nafaqat grammatik aniqlikni, balki tezlik, tabiiylik va ifoda qulayligini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Bu fikrlarni samarali va ishonchli tarzda yetkazishdir. Grammatik aniqlik muhim bo'lsada, faqat unga e'tibor qaratish ravonlik rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, ingliz tilida erkin gapira olish — bu murakkab, ammo o'rgatiladigan ko'nikma. O'qituvchi darsda interaktiv, muammoli va texnologik yondashuvlarni uyg'un qo'llasa, o'quvchilar nutq jarayonida ishonchli, ravon va faol bo'la boshlaydi. Gapirishni faollashtirish uchun darslar o'quvchi markazli bo'lishi, fikr almashinuvi, ijodkorlik va real hayotga bog'lanishi kerak. Shu tarzda o'quvchilar tilni nafaqat bilishadi, balki u bilan yashay boshlashadi.

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MADANIYATLARARO DIALOGNI TA'MINLASHNING FENOMENOLOGIK JIHALARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola madaniyatlararo dialogning fenomenologik mohiyatini falsafiy va tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qiladi. Dialog faqat til vositasi orqali yuzaga keladigan muloqot shakli emas, balki shaxslarning ongli faoliyati va madaniy tajribalari o'zaro tan olinadigan tushunish maydonidir. Maqolada tilning semantik qatlamlari, anglash jarayonining intersub'yektiv tabiati va madaniy kontekstlararo tafovutlarning qanday qilib muloqot jarayoniga ta'sir qilishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, sharq va g'arb tafakkur tarzida madaniyatlar dialog, madaniyatlararo aloqada fenomenologik yondashuvning ahamiyatini ochib berilgan va tilni nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki tajribaga bog'liq fenomenologik mohiyati asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo dialog, fenomenologiya, til falsafasi, anglash, semantika, intersub'yektivlik, madaniy tafovut.

PHENOMENOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ENSURING INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE

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Abstract. This article analyzes the phenomenological essence of intercultural dialogue from philosophical and linguistic perspectives. Dialogue is not merely a form of communication established through language, but rather a field of mutual understanding in which the mental and cultural experiences of individuals are acknowledged and engaged. The article explores the semantic layers of language, the intersubjective nature of the process of understanding, and the impact of cultural contextual differences on communication. Furthermore, it highlights the significance of the phenomenological approach in intercultural relations by examining dialogue between Eastern and Western modes of thought. Language is presented not only as a tool of communication but also as a phenomenon rooted in experiential meaning.

Keywords: intercultural dialogue, phenomenology, philosophy of language, understanding, semantics, intersubjectivity, cultural differences.

Zamonaviy globallashuv davrida insonlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunish va madaniy hamkorlikni ta'minlash zarurati ortib bormoqda. Madaniyatlararo dialog – bu turli sivilizatsiyalar, urf-odatlar va axloqiy me'yorlar o'rtasidagi tushunishga asoslangan muloqotdir. Biroq bunday muloqot yuzaki til almashinuvi emas, balki har ikki tomonning dunyoni idrok etish, anglash va talqin qilish tarzlarining o'zaro moslashuvidir. Shu sababli, madaniyatlararo dialogning tub mohiyatini anglashda fenomenologik yondashuv muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Falsafiy fenomenologiya – xususan, Edmund Husserl, Martin Heidegger va Hans-Georg Gadamer asarlarida – til va anglashning o'zaro bog'liqligini chuqur tahlil qiladi. Shu bilan birga, tilshunoslikda ham kommunikativ pragmatika, semantik tafovut va tilning madaniy kodlari bilan bog'liq yondashuvlar madaniyatlararo tushunishni chuqurroq anglashga imkon beradi.

Fenomenologiyada dialog – bu ikki subyekt o'rtasidagi intersubyektiv tajriba almashinuvining maydonidir. Husserlga ko'ra, inson subyektiv tajribalari orqali dunyoni “ma'no bilan yuklaydi”, ya'ni har bir inson o'z madaniy, tarixiy, til va estetik tajribasidan kelib chiqqan holda voqelikni talqin qiladi. Madaniyatlararo dialogda esa bu ma'nolar kesishadi, to'qnashadi yoki uyg'unlashadi. Shu bois dialogning muvaffaqiyati har ikki tomonning “boshqa” subyekt nuqtai nazarini tushunish va qabul qilishga tayyorligiga bog'liq.

Til – bu faqat axborot uzatish vositasi emas, balki madaniy identitet va tajribaning semantik shakllanishi vositasidir. Tilshunoslikda semantik tafovut, kontekstual ma'no va pragmatik tushuncha aynan madaniyatlararo muloqotda muhim o'rin tutadi. Misol uchun, bir madaniyatda “erkinlik” yoki “hurmat” tushunchasi boshqa madaniyatda tamoman boshqa emotsional yoki ijtimoiy yuklama bilan anglanishi mumkin. Shunday holatda til orqali muloqotda turli semantik sohalar o'rtasida “ma'no muvofiqlashtiruv” (semantic negotiation) sodir bo'ladi. Gadamer (1975) o'zining “Hermenevtika va haqiqat” asarida tushunishni til orqali amalga oshadigan “boshqa”ni anglash amaliyoti sifatida tavsiflaydi.

Til – bu faqat axborot uzatish vositasi emas, balki madaniy identitet va tajribaning semantik shakllanishi vositasidir. Tilshunoslikda semantik tafovut, kontekstual ma'no va pragmatik tushuncha aynan madaniyatlararo muloqotda muhim o'rin tutadi. Misol uchun, bir madaniyatda "erkinlik" yoki "hurmat" tushunchasi boshqa madaniyatda tamoman boshqa emotsional yoki ijtimoiy yuklama bilan anglanishi mumkin. Shunday holatda til orqali muloqotda turli semantik sohalar o'rtasida “ma'no muvofiqlashtiruv” (semantic negotiation) sodir bo'ladi.

Gadamer (1975) o'zining “Hermenevtika va haqiqat” asarida tushunishni til orqali amalga oshadigan “boshqa”ni anglash amaliyoti sifatida tavsiflaydi. Madaniyatlararo dialogda bu jarayon nafaqat tarjima, balki madaniy adaptatsiyani ham talab qiladi. Martin Xaydegger tilni “bo'lishning uyi” deb atagan. Bu yondashuvga

ko'ra, inson voqelikni til orqali ongda quradi. Har bir til o'ziga xos ontologik dunyo tasvirini beradi. Demak, madaniyatlararo dialog bu ikki xil "ontologik xarita" o'rtasidagi aloqani o'rnatish, tafakkurni bir-biriga yaqinlashtirishdir. Bu yerda tarjima yoki har qanday asarning mohiyati nafaqat lug'aviy darajada, balki kontekstual, konnotativ va aksiologik darajalarda ham amalga oshirilishi zarur. Faqat shunda madaniyatlararo anglash chuqur va real bo'ladi. O'zbek she'riyati misolida fenomenologik tahlilni amalga oshiramiz.

O'zbek she'riyatida o'z o'rniga ega kuchli falsafiy g'oyalarni ilgari surgan Abdulla Oripov she'rlaridagi madaniyatlararo dialogga asoslangan, o'zbek xalqining irodasini aks ettiradigan "Iltimos" nomli she'rining yakuniy ikki misrasini dastlab O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati asosida ayrim so'zlarini tahlil qilsak:

Mening bir jaydari falsafamdir shu:

Hargiz iltimosga kuning qolmasin.

Jaydari	Oddiy, sodda inson
Falsafa	shaxsiy tajriba, fikr-o'y asosida yuzaga kelgan ishonch, e'tiqod.
Hargiz	Aslo, sira, hech
Iltimos	Muddaoni (maqsad, istakni) qondirish haqida qilingan murojaat, so'rash.

Fenomenologik yondashuv orqali esa, asosiy e'tibor voqelikning qanday "ko'rinishi"ga, ya'ni inson ongida u qanday namoyon bo'lishiga qaratiladi. "iltimos qilish" – bu shunchaki nutqiy harakat emas, balki subyektning o'z ehtiyoji yoki zaifligini boshqaga tan olishi orqali yuzaga keladigan ontologik holatdir. Bu holat Gusserl terminologiyasida "intensional akt" bo'lib, tashqi dunyoga yo'naltirilgan ongiy harakatdir. Demak, bu jumlada inson o'zini boshqa subyektga qaratishga tayyor emasligini, balki ichki avtonomiyaga asoslangan bo'lishni istashini ifoda etadi. Gusserlning Lebenswelt – ya'ni "hayotiy dunyo" tushunchasi bo'yicha, har bir inson o'zining individual dunyo tajribasida harakat qiladi. "Hargiz iltimosga kuning qolmasin" degan ibora, shaxsning boshqalar irodasiga tobe bo'lmagan, ichki avtonom, va ijtimoiy munosabatlarda passiv emas, faol subyekt bo'lib yashash istagini bildiradi. Bu esa uning hayotiy dunyosida "iltimos" qilish holati salbiy, zaiflik bilan bog'liq sifatida tajribalanayotganini ko'rsatadi. Martin Xaydegger fenomenologik ekzistensializm da insonning "dunyo ichra bo'lishi"ni (In-der-Welt-sein) asosiy mavjudlik holati deb ataydi. "Iltimosga ko'nish" – bu mavjudlikning boshqasiga qaratilgan, qisman cheklangan shakli. Jumlada keltirilgan fikr esa sub'yektning o'z mavjudligini boshqaga qaram bo'lmagan holatda saqlab qolishga urinishidir.

Fenomenologik nuqtai nazardan qaralganda, har qanday ijtimoiy munosabat — bu onglararo dialog (intersubektivlik) maydonidir. Ushbu jumla esa bu dialogga kirishga tayyor emaslik, yoki bu dialogda pastki pozitsiyani egallamaslik istagini bildiradi. Ya'ni, bu yerda sub'yekt dialogga faqat barobar asosda kirishga tayyor, aks holda — rad qiladi. Bu esa uning ijtimoiy va axloqiy ongida irodaviy mustahkamlik, passiv emas, faol pozitsiya egallash tamoyiliga urg'u berilganini bildiradi. "Hargiz iltimosga kuning qolmasin" — bu ibora fenomenologik tahlilda ontologik mustaqillik, inson qadr-qimmatini, va hayotiy dunyoda zaif emas, faol subyekt bo'lib yashash istagini ifodalaydi. U ijtimoiy muloqotdagi o'ziga xos yondashuvni, ichki axloqiy holatni va hayotiy pozitsiyani ochib beradi. Bu falsafiy pozitsiya subyektga nisbatan boshqalarning nazari, irodasi yoki rahmiga suyanmasdan, o'z qarorlarining ongli egasi bo'lishga da'vatdir.

Globalashuv sharoitida madaniyatlararo muloqot insoniyat taraqqiyotining ajralmas tarkibiy qismiga aylanmoqda. Turli madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi to'qnashuv yoki o'zaro tushunmovchiliklar ko'pincha universal insoniy qadriyatlar va ong tajribasining to'g'ri anglanmasligidan kelib chiqadi. Fenomenologiya vositasida esa inson tajribasiga tayangan holda madaniyatlararo dialogni tushunish va rivojlantirishda muhim nazariy poydevor shakllantirish mumkin.

Xulosa. Madaniyatlararo dialogning muvaffaqiyati, avvalo, subyektlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro anglashuvga tayangan holda shakllanadi. Falsafiy fenomenologiya va zamonaviy tilshunoslik integratsiyasi orqali bu jarayon yanada chuqurroq anglanadi. Dialog — bu faqat so'z almashinuvi emas, balki ikki madaniyatning o'zaro tan olinishi, tajriba almashuvi va ma'no yaratish jarayonidir. Til — bu ong, madaniyat va identitetning tashuvchisi bo'lib, madaniyatlararo dialogni semantik, aksiologik va kommunikativ jihatdan yo'naltiradi. Shunday ekan, madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish uchun nafaqat til bilimi, balki madaniy semantikani anglash, intersubektiv ochiqlik va falsafiy empatiya zarur hisoblanadi.

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A COMPREHENSIVE FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATING THE FOUR MACRO – SKILLS WITH VOCABULARY GRAMMAR IN UZBEK ELT

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Abstract: Reforms in Uzbek English classes in recent years have increased student motivation, but they have also exposed enduring deficiencies in speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. A thorough examination of national policy initiatives, theoretical foundations, scaffolded teaching strategies, technology integration, assessment procedures, and solutions for typical classroom problems can be found in this article.

Keywords: English language teaching, Uzbekistan, educational reform, language skills, scaffolded instruction, technology integration, classroom challenges, assessment.

Annotatsiya: So‘nggi yillarda O‘zbekistonda ingliz tilini o‘qitishdagi islohotlar o‘quvchilar motivatsiyasini sezilarli darajada oshirdi. Shu bilan birga, bu islohotlar gapirish, tinglab tushunish, o‘qish va yozish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi mavjud muammolarni ham ochib berdi. Ushbu maqolada milliy ta‘lim siyosati, til o‘qitishning nazariy asoslari, bosqichma-bosqich o‘qitish usullari, dars jarayonida texnologiyalardan foydalanish, baholash tizimi va darsda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal qilish bo‘yicha yechimlar chuqur tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ingliz tilini o‘qitish, O‘zbekiston, ta‘lim islohotlari, til ko‘nikmalari, bosqichma-bosqich o‘qitish, texnologiyalarni joriy etish, sinfdagi muammolar, baholash.

Аннотация: Недавние реформы в преподавании английского языка в Узбекистане значительно повысили мотивацию студентов. Однако эти реформы также выявили устойчивые проблемы в развитии навыков говорения, аудирования, чтения и письма. В статье проводится всесторонний анализ национальной образовательной политики, теоретических основ преподавания языков, поэтапных методов обучения, интеграции технологий, процедур оценки и решений типичных проблем в учебных аудиториях.

Ключевые слова: Преподавание английского языка, Узбекистан, образовательные реформы, языковые навыки, поэтапное обучение, интеграция технологий, проблемы в классе, оценивание.

According to a national language policy, English instruction now starts in the earliest grades, and many jobs and university admission require proficiency certificates. Many students still find it difficult to advance past basic survival English in spite of these efforts. The scaffolding that students require to progress is created by

integrating focused vocabulary development and grammar practice into each lesson while simultaneously fostering the development of all four skills.

Through collaborations with a number of foreign organizations, the Ministry of Education has updated school facilities, retrained teachers, and modernized curricula. While many rural schools lack even basic audio players, urban schools frequently have dependable internet, multimedia labs, and knowledgeable teachers. Instruction must combine high-tech resources like online discussion boards and mobile listening platforms with low-tech activities like paired oral drills and printed vocabulary journals to guarantee that all students gain.

Communicative methods prioritize fluency and meaningful interaction over memorization. Task-based approaches use real-world projects to organically incorporate grammar and vocabulary into skill practice. Cognitive psychology insights remind us to gradually increase task complexity in order to manage learners' mental workload. Language acquisition theories place a strong emphasis on opportunities to produce language in supportive settings and on comprehensible input, which is reading or listening content that is just a little bit above a learner's current proficiency level.

Thematic word families and high-frequency wordlists provide students with the fuel they need to understand and communicate. Teaching common collocations encourages native-like phrasing (e.g., "undertake a project" instead of "do a project"). The most successful grammar lessons follow a pattern that involves introducing a structure, guiding practice in controlled exercises, and then communicative tasks where students apply the form in authentic situations.

Students are exposed to natural speech patterns and vocabulary through authentic audio, such as news segments, podcasts, and short films. Learners concentrate on the overall meaning during passive-listening sessions, which reduces anxiety. They complete structured notes (main idea, supporting details, unfamiliar words), transcribe passages, and respond to comprehension questions in active-listening exercises. Learners gain confidence and proficiency when important vocabulary is pre-taught and the audio's speed or complexity is progressively increased.

Effective reading instruction combines pre-reading tasks that introduce essential lexis and activate background knowledge, with timed skimming and scanning drills to locate gist and details quickly. Extensive reading of graded texts and short articles encourages fluency and incidental vocabulary growth. Classroom libraries stocked with leveled books, reading journals for vocabulary logs, and annotation exercises for inferencing sharpen critical-reading abilities.

A process-writing cycle starts with mind mapping and brainstorming to organise ideas, then moves on to model analysis of excellent essays to identify logical structure and cohesive devices, and finally ends with draughting on collaborative

platforms where peers provide structured feedback. After that, teachers offer focused advice on local grammar or word choice problems as well as global organization. Students can view their own progress through portfolios that contain multiple drafts.

Role-plays, debates, and information-gap exercises are low-stakes group and pair activities that allow students to practice speaking English without worrying about receiving harsh criticism. Instant visual and aural feedback on specific sounds and stress patterns is provided by pronunciation apps. Learners can better absorb natural intonation and linking by observing brief speeches or dialogues (such as short presentations by native speakers). Reflecting on and recording student presentations fosters metacognitive awareness.

Reading research articles, writing abstracts, listening to peer presentations, and giving one's own talk are all part of project-based assignments, like planning a mini-conference with a cultural theme. Interactive tests for formative assessments and digital collaboration tools for brainstorming make sure that all four skills, as well as the targeted vocabulary and grammar structures, are practiced in a real-world setting.

Teachers can quickly modify their instruction with the support of ongoing formative checks, such as exit tickets, short vocabulary tests, and self-assessment checklists that are in line with can-do statements. Students get a clear picture of their overall proficiency through regular mock exams or classroom benchmarks. Actionable insights are the main focus of feedback, which includes providing example reformulations for ambiguous sentences, employing shorthand error codes for common grammar errors, and praising clear communication to keep motivation high.

A blended-learning ecosystem combines spaced-repetition flashcard apps for targeted vocabulary review, online language databases for authentic example sentences, learning-management platforms for distributing multimedia materials and discussion forums, and video-conference links for virtual interactions with native speakers. Such tools extend learning beyond the classroom and encourage independent study habits.

Resource disparities and gaps in teacher training are addressed through national communities of practice, peer mentoring, and ongoing professional-development workshops on communicative and task-based methodologies. Open-access repositories for lesson plans, video demonstrations, and annotated materials make high-quality resources more accessible. Coaching students on goal setting and portfolio maintenance promotes learner autonomy.

Every lesson should be scaffolded so that vocabulary and grammar are integrated into all listening, reading, writing, and speaking activities. Combining low-tech oral drills and journals with high-tech apps and online corpora ensures equitable access. Adopt project-based tasks to reflect real-life communication. Implement

continuous formative assessment to guide both the teacher and the learner. Invest in ongoing teacher training and digital infrastructure, particularly in underserved areas.

A truly integrated approach—one that incorporates targeted vocabulary work and focused grammar practice into all listening, reading, writing, and speaking activities—creates the conditions for consistent, long-term progress. When teachers design lessons around authentic communication tasks, challenge students gradually, and provide timely, actionable feedback, students gain both confidence and competence in using English outside of the classroom. Uzbek learners can progress from basic survival English to fluent, flexible communication by combining simple, low-tech routines with carefully selected digital resources, as well as encouraging a culture of goal-setting and self-reflection. This holistic framework has the potential to transform English learning into a dynamic, empowering journey, rather than a series of disconnected drills.

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INTEGRATING PRONUNCIATION PRACTICE INTO PUBLIC SPEAKING TRAINING FOR EFL LEARNERS

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Abstract

This article investigates how incorporating pronunciation practice into public speaking training can improve the oral communication skills of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students. The significance of segmental and suprasegmental features such as stress, intonation, and rhythm in relation to speech clarity and audience engagement is emphasized. The paper discusses teaching techniques, classroom strategies, and technological tools for improving pronunciation during public speaking.

Keywords: Pronunciation, Public Speaking, EFL Learners, Oral Communication.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается, как интеграция практики произношения в обучение публичным выступлениям может улучшить устные коммуникативные навыки изучающих английский язык как иностранный. Особое внимание уделяется важности сегментных и супrasegmentных особенностей, таких как ударение, интонация и ритм, а также их влиянию на ясность речи и вовлечение аудитории. Описываются методы преподавания, стратегии в классе и технологические инструменты, направленные на развитие произношения в контексте публичных выступлений.

Ключевые слова: Произношение, Публичные выступления, Изучающие английский язык, Устная речь.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada talaffuz mashqlarini ommaviy nutq mashg'ulotlariga integratsiyalash orqali ingliz tilini o'rganayotgan talabalar og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari yoritiladi. Segment va suprasegment xususiyatlar, ya'ni urg'u, intonatsiya va ritm kabi elementlarning nutq ravonligiga va tinglovchilar e'tiboriga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, sinfda qo'llaniladigan o'qitish usullari, texnologik vositalar va amaliy yondashuvlar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Talaffuz, Ommaviy nutq, Ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari, Og'zaki nutq, O'qitish strategiyalari.

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students frequently face significant challenges in oral communication, particularly when giving public speeches. One of the most significant challenges is a lack of accurate pronunciation, which directly affects intelligibility, listener comprehension, and the learner's overall confidence. Inadequate pronunciation can cause misunderstandings, anxiety, and impede the learner's ability to effectively engage an audience. Because public speaking is both a linguistic activity and a performance skill, the ability to deliver a clear, fluent, and well-pronounced speech is essential. To effectively convey meaning and engage the

audience, it is necessary to use rhythm, intonation, stress, and pauses in addition to accurate sound articulation.

Public speaking necessitates a combination of cognitive, linguistic, and non-linguistic abilities. This includes an understanding of vocabulary, sentence structure, body language, eye contact, and emotional expression. Among these, pronunciation is critical because it ensures that the message is clearly understood and that the speaker connects with the audience. Furthermore, clear pronunciation increases the speaker's credibility and authority, both of which are necessary for making a lasting impression during a presentation.

Integrating pronunciation practice into public speaking training takes a comprehensive approach to improving speaking abilities. Focussing on pronunciation in the context of public speaking training entails more than simply teaching students how to produce sounds correctly. It also entails teaching them the rhythm and patterns of English speech, which are essential for effective oral communication. This method ensures that pronunciation instruction is embedded in the communicative context of real-life speaking scenarios, such as speeches, debates, and presentations.

Pronunciation has long been recognized as an important aspect of spoken language proficiency in any language learning setting. However, it is frequently overlooked in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction due to a variety of challenges. These challenges include time constraints in the classroom, insufficient teacher training, and an overemphasis on other language skills such as grammar, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. Despite these challenges, research consistently emphasizes the importance of pronunciation for effective communication, especially in public speaking situations. According to Celce-Murcia, effective pronunciation instruction should focus on both segmental and suprasegmental features, which contribute to EFL speakers' overall intelligibility and fluency. These elements are essential not only for everyday communication but also for public speaking, where clarity of speech, effective delivery, and audience engagement are all critical. The incorporation of pronunciation practice into public speaking training can provide significant benefits to EFL learners by improving both speech accuracy and the ability to convey meaning in an engaging and understandable manner.

Segmental features are the individual speech sounds, such as vowels and consonants. While segmental are frequently the first point of emphasis in pronunciation instruction, they are equally important for public speaking as they are for everyday conversation. Segments are the fundamental building blocks of spoken language, and their proper production is critical for clarity.

In public speaking situations, mispronouncing segmental features can cause confusion or miscommunication. For example, a minor misarticulation of vowels or consonants can lead to a word being misunderstood or the speaker being difficult to

understand. For example, confusion between the sounds of "ship" and "sheep," or "cot" and "caught," can significantly alter the meaning of a speaker's message. To address these issues, EFL learners' pronunciation training should include activities focusing on problematic sounds. Minimal pair drills (e.g., "bat" vs. "pat") can help students distinguish between sounds that may not be present in their native language, reducing the likelihood of confusion. These exercises, when combined with repetition practice, can improve learners' ability to produce individual sounds, resulting in clearer, more intelligible speech in public settings.

Suprasegmental features are aspects of speech that go beyond individual sounds, such as **stress**, **intonation**, and **rhythm**. These elements are essential for effective communication, particularly in public speaking, where delivery is as important as content. While segmental concentrate on the accuracy of individual sounds, suprasegmental control the **flow** and **expressiveness** of speech, which contributes to the overall intelligibility, emotion, and emphasis conveyed to the audience.

Stress is the emphasis placed on specific syllables or words within an utterance. In English, stress is frequently used to convey meaning, distinguish between nouns and verbs (e.g., CONTRACT vs. conTRACT), and emphasize important information. In public speaking, strategically using stress can help the speaker direct the audience's attention to key points, making the message clearer and more persuasive. EFL learners frequently struggle with stress patterns, especially if their native language does not use stress in the same way as English. This can result in monotonous or unnatural speech that does not capture the audience's attention. To address this, pronunciation practice in public should concentrate on word stress (emphasizing syllables within words) and sentence stress (emphasizing specific words in a sentence to convey meaning and emotion).

Intonation is the rising and falling pitch of a speaker's voice as they deliver a sentence. It is essential for conveying the emotional tone of the speech, indicating questions or statements, and clarifying meaning. For example, rising intonation at the end of a sentence can indicate a question, whereas falling intonation usually indicates a statement or thought completion.

Poor or incorrect intonation in public speaking can result in flat or robotic speech that may disengage the audience. EFL learners frequently struggle to master English intonation patterns, which can differ significantly from those in their native languages. Incorporating **intonation practice** into public speaking training can help students improve their ability to express emotion, convey nuances, and engage their audience more effectively.

In spoken language, rhythm refers to the pattern of stressed and unstressed syllables, as well as the overall timing of speech. English has a stress-timed rhythm,

which means that stressed syllables appear at roughly equal intervals of time, while unstressed syllables have a shorter, more variable duration. This rhythm is essential for natural-sounding English speech and helps with public speaking.

Many EFL students, particularly those from languages with syllable-timed rhythms (such as Spanish and French), may struggle with the timing and flow of English speech. A mismatch between the learner's native rhythm and the English stress-timed rhythm can produce speech that sounds awkward or labored. Practicing rhythmic reading and speech drills can help learners internalize the rhythm of English, resulting in smoother and more fluent public speaking.

The effective integration of segmental and suprasegmental features has a significant impact on EFL learners' public speaking success. When students can accurately reproduce both the sounds (segmental) and the melody and flow of English speech (suprasegmental), they are more likely to:

Improve intelligibility: Effective communication depends on the audience being able to understand the speaker's point with little effort thanks to clear pronunciation.

Boost confidence: Learners are more likely to interact with the audience and give a persuasive speech when they are comfortable with their pronunciation.

Increase audience engagement: The speech is more captivating and the audience is kept interested by the skillful use of stress, intonation, and rhythm.

Develop credibility: Pronouncing words clearly and confidently increases the speaker's authority and dependability, which is crucial in public speaking situations where influence and persuasion are crucial.

For a number of reasons, pronunciation is frequently overlooked in EFL classes despite its significance. Teachers who have not received sufficient professional development in this area or who have not received formal training in phonetics may feel unprepared to offer focused pronunciation instruction. Furthermore, pronunciation drills can take a lot of time and constant focus, which can be difficult in a busy curriculum.

To get around these issues, educators can include pronunciation drills into routine public speaking activities, giving students regular, continuous feedback on how they pronounce words. Teachers can also help students practice outside of class and monitor their progress over time by using technology, such as online pronunciation tools or speech recognition software. Working together with linguistic specialists or speech therapists can improve the quality of pronunciation instruction, providing teachers with additional resources and expertise. EFL learners can improve their spoken language proficiency, boost their self-confidence, and interact with audiences more effectively by addressing both segmental and suprasegmental aspects in public speaking training. Correct sound production is only one aspect of pronunciation;

another is conveying a message in a way that is understandable, engaging, and focused on the listener.

A thorough and methodical approach to improving EFL learners' oral communication abilities is to incorporate pronunciation practice into public speaking instruction. Combining public speaking with pronunciation, which is frequently isolated as a separate or secondary component of traditional language instruction, enables contextualized, purposeful learning that mirrors the demands of real-world communication. In addition to linguistic accuracy, public speaking calls for clarity, fluency, confidence, and audience participation—all of which are strongly impacted by pronunciation.

Teachers can help students become more proficient at delivering meaning in entire utterances by specifically addressing both segmental (like vowel and consonant sounds) and suprasegmental (like stress, intonation, and rhythm) aspects. While mastery of suprasegmental features enables learners to sound more natural, expressive, and persuasive—skills that are crucial in public speaking contexts—segmental accuracy improves intelligibility at the word level. In conclusion, pronunciation-focused public speaking instruction develops critical communication skills that go beyond the classroom while also giving EFL students the means to communicate more effectively and fluently. It increases linguistic confidence, strengthens the bond between the speaker and the audience, and gets students ready for a variety of speaking scenarios in the real world, such as business meetings and academic presentations. This integrated approach provides a significant route to genuine communicative competence as clarity and credibility are valued more and more in global communication.

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Beyond the traditional view: fluency as a multifaceted construct

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Abstract

Fluency in second language acquisition (SLA) has drawn attention from both pedagogical and scholarly angles, considering that it deeply impacts communicative competence. Educators want to understand fluency in order to improve their students' performance, while researchers focus on its multifaceted nature. "Fluency: The ability to produce spoken language effortlessly, quickly, and with limited pauses", tends to be viewed through a more conceptual lens as a result of cognitive and emotional factors, as well as context. For scope, the aim of this article is to pull together perspectives from existing literature on the concept of fluency to produce a more flexible understanding, provide efficacious teaching techniques, and formulate new paths for exploration.

Key words: fluency, techniques, instruction, complex, speech, interactive, communication, tools.

Annotatsiya

Ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish (ITO) jarayonida ravonlik ham pedagogik, ham ilmiy nuqtai nazardan katta e'tiborni jalb qilmoqda, chunki u muloqot qobiliyatiga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatadi. O'qituvchilar talabalarining natijalarini yaxshilash uchun ravonlikni tushunishga intilsalar, tadqiqotchilar uning ko'p qirrali tabiati bilan shug'ullanadilar. "Ravonlik: so'zlashuv tilini oson, tez va kam tanaffuslar bilan ishlab chiqish qobiliyati" – bu tushuncha ko'proq kognitiv, emotsional va kontekstual omillar tufayli nazariy nuqtai nazardan ko'riladi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi – mavjud adabiyotdagi ravonlik haqidagi qarashlarni birlashtirib, yanada moslashuvchan tushuncha yaratish, samarali o'qitish uslublarini taklif qilish va yangi tadqiqot yo'nalishlarini shakllantirishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: ravonlik, texnikalar, yo'riqnoma, murakkab, nutq, interaktiv, muloqot, vosita.

Аннотация

Беглость речи в изучении второго языка привлекла внимание как и со стороны педагогов, так и со стороны ученых, которые считают, что она глубоко воздействует на коммуникативную компетентность. Преподаватели хотят понять этот концепт, чтобы улучшить прогресс своих студентов, в то время как исследователей интересует его многокомпонентность. Беглость: способность производить устную речь легко быстро и с минимальным количеством пауз, рассматривается с концептуальной точки зрения в силу когнитивных и

эмоциональных факторов, и контекста. Целью данной статьи является объединить точки зрения имеющейся литературы о концепте беглости чтобы привнести необходимую гибкости в понимание, предоставить эффективные методы обучения, и сформулировать новые сферы для исследования.

Ключевые слова: беглость, техника, инструкция, комплексный, речь, интерактивный, коммуникация, инструменты.

Foster (2020), advocates for more contemporary definitions of oral fluency arguing from her works that studying speech rate and frequency of pauses does not directly address the underlying aspects of speaking fluently. She places emphasis on the need to analyze the use of language in real time interaction capturing fluency as a participatory, contextual phenomenon. Also embracing this complexity, Peltonen (2024) approaches fluency with consideration of core principles of ELT, advising that it is far more complex than speed or smoothness, but refers rather to degree of acceptability, adaptability and intended message. These perspectives enable teacher to take a broader look at classroom practices and emphasize the interaction between learners.

Recent studies highlight that learners' fluency is impacted by a range of internal and external factors. Wang, Rezaei, and Izadpanah (2024) study the role of creative thinking, emotional intelligence, and academic interest on fluency and accuracy. Their results suggest that emotionally intelligent and creative learners tend to produce more fluent and accurate speech because they are more capable of managing their emotions and focusing on language tasks. These findings support broader calls to teach socio-emotional skills through language classes.

In another important contribution, Gao and Sun (2023) conduct a meta-analysis on the relation between L1 and L2 fluency and find some L1 fluency behaviors might predict similar L2 fluency behaviors. Their work proposes that fluency might not be totally bound to a language, but rather to general cognitive-linguistic systems underlying languages.

Because fluency is multifaceted, the approach taken to teach it has to be equally multi-faceted. In Yufriзал's (2018) work, the 4/3/2 technique, which is specific to pedagogy, has been examined. This technique requires students to repeat a certain speech thrice with each attempt separated by a time limit (first executed in four minutes, followed by three, and then two). This time compression encourages learners to optimize their outputs, reducing pauses and increasing automatic responses. Findings from some EFL classrooms in Indonesia suggest that this method fosters growth in speaking fluency, especially in the rapidity and logical sequencing of ideas.

Dynamic assessment (DA) is another promising approach. In their publication with Cogent Education in 2020, researchers analyzed the case of pre-intermediate EFL

learners and assessed the impact of DA on speaking accuracy and fluency. DA intertwines evaluation with instruction, actively monitoring progress to fill performance gaps and to foster learner independence. Students who received DA showed greater improvement than students who received traditional forms of instruction, demonstrating the need for responsive and formative feedback in developing fluency skills.

The 2024 International Journal of Social Science and Human Research highlights methods like task-based learning, storytelling, and peer interaction. These methods are meant to lower affective filters, raise learner involvement, encourage learners to use the language spontaneously, and are all helpful in the development of fluency.

Götz (2013) has captured in detail the discourse-level differences in the use of English between native and non-native speakers' language fluency. Apart from the more temporal measures (speed, pausing), she highlights differences in discourse-level features like the variety of vocabulary used in phrases and the level of complexity in the grammar employed. It would be prudent to consider her suggestion, which is that fluency instruction need not emphasize the native-like execution of such performance thresholds, but rather aim for functional adequacy within defined contexts of communication. Other studies have reiterated this stance arguing for focusing on the intelligibility of the speech and comfortability of the listener as opposed to native-like norms.

Foster (2020) highlights a critical gap in the literature that needs further address: the investigation of the live processes of executing speech and the interactions that come along with it in the real world. Using more advanced means of data capture like eye tracking and speech-recognition technology might reveal even more intricate data patterns. Alongside these gaps, there is sparse data on the longitudinal tracking of the development of fluency across different environments. Lastly, gaps remain for study on the impacts of digital technology, especially AI-powered feedback systems.

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Key Terminology in Internal Auditing In English: A Beginner’s Glossary

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Abstract. Internal auditing is a cornerstone of effective governance and risk management in modern organizations. However, the technical vocabulary used by internal auditors can be a barrier for students, junior staff, and non-audit professionals. This paper presents a structured glossary of fundamental internal audit terminology, contextualized within theoretical and practical frameworks. The objective is to demystify audit language and support foundational learning in the field. Using a literature review and a qualitative analysis of common audit reports and guidance from the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), this study identifies and defines over 40 essential terms. Terms are grouped by thematic relevance to audit processes—planning, execution, reporting, and follow-up—and accompanied by examples. The results demonstrate how clarity in terminology enhances understanding, facilitates communication, and improves audit performance. The glossary aims to serve both as a pedagogical tool and a reference for beginners.

Keywords: Internal audit, audit terminology, glossary, audit education, governance, risk management, internal controls, audit training.

Аннотация. Внутренний аудит является краеугольным камнем эффективного управления и управления рисками в современных организациях. Однако технический словарь, используемый внутренними аудиторами, может быть барьером для студентов, младшего персонала и неаудиторских специалистов. В этой статье представлен структурированный глоссарий фундаментальной терминологии внутреннего аудита, контекстуализированный в теоретических и практических рамках. Цель состоит в том, чтобы демистифицировать язык аудита и поддержать фундаментальное обучение в этой области. Используя обзор литературы и качественный анализ общих аудиторских отчетов и рекомендаций Института внутренних аудиторов (IIA), в этом исследовании идентифицируется и определяется более 40 основных терминов. Термины сгруппированы по тематической значимости для аудиторских процессов — планирование, выполнение, отчетность и последующие действия — и сопровождаются примерами. Результаты показывают, как ясность терминологии улучшает понимание, облегчает общение и повышает эффективность аудита. Глоссарий призван служить как педагогическим инструментом, так и справочником для начинающих.

Ключевые слова: Внутренний аудит, терминология аудита, глоссарий, аудиторское образование, управление, управление рисками, внутренний контроль, аудиторское обучение

Annotatsiya. Ichki audit zamonaviy tashkilotlarda samarali boshqaruv va risklarni boshqarishning asosidir. Biroq, ichki auditorlar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan texnik lug'at talabalar, kichik xodimlar va auditor bo'lmagan mutaxassislar uchun to'siq bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada asosiy ichki audit atamalarining tuzilgan lug'ati mavjud bo'lib, ular nazariy va amaliy doirada kontekstga ega. Maqsad audit tilini yo'q qilish va bu sohada asosiy o'rganishni qo'llab-quvvatlashdir. Adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish va umumiy audit hisobotlarini sifatli tahlil qilish va Ichki Auditorlar Instituti (IIA) ko'rsatmalaridan foydalangan holda, ushbu tadqiqot 40 dan ortiq muhim atamalarni aniqlaydi va belgilaydi. Atamalar audit jarayonlariga - rejalashtirish, bajarish, hisobot berish va kuzatish - mavzuga mos ravishda guruhlangan va misollar bilan birga keltirilgan. Natijalar atamalarning ravshanligi tushunishni kuchaytirishi, mulqotni osonlashtirishi va audit samaradorligini oshirishini ko'rsatadi. Lug'at ham pedagogik vosita, ham yangi boshlanuvchilar uchun ma'lumotnoma sifatida xizmat qilishni maqsad qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ichki audit, audit terminologiyasi, lug'at, audit ta'limi, boshqaruv, risklarni boshqarish, ichki nazorat, auditorlik treningi.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Internal auditing has evolved from a compliance-focused function to a strategic tool for governance, risk management, and internal control enhancement. As the scope and influence of internal audit grow, so does the complexity of its language. Internal audit reports, risk matrices, control evaluations, and audit planning documents are rich in technical jargon that, while precise for professionals, can be difficult to interpret for non-specialists.

Understanding audit terminology is a foundational requirement for those entering the profession and for other stakeholders who interact with audit teams. Without a clear grasp of key terms, the value of internal audit can be misunderstood or underutilized. This issue is particularly relevant in educational contexts, where students are first introduced to auditing principles.

1.2 Research Problem

While professional bodies like the IIA publish standards and glossaries, there remains a gap in literature that organizes key terms in a pedagogically effective format tailored for beginners. Furthermore, much of the available terminology lacks contextual examples or structured explanations linking the terms to the audit process.

1.3 Purpose and Objectives

This article seeks to create an accessible glossary of internal audit terminology aimed at beginners. The objectives are:

- To identify and define essential internal audit terms used in professional practice.
- To categorize these terms according to phases of the audit cycle.
- To provide usage context and examples for each term.

- To support teaching and early-stage learning of internal auditing concepts.

1.4 Significance

This glossary supports educators, students, junior auditors, and cross-functional teams in enhancing their audit literacy. By providing a structured vocabulary base, it lays the foundation for deeper engagement with auditing standards and techniques.

2. Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study employs a qualitative content analysis methodology. It combines literature review and document analysis of audit reports, internal audit manuals, and the IIA's glossary of terms. The goal is not merely to extract definitions, but to contextualize and explain them in a learning-friendly manner.

2.2 Data Sources

Primary sources include:

- The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) International Professional Practices Framework (IPPF)
- Selected academic textbooks on internal auditing
- Publicly available internal audit reports from corporations and public institutions
- Educational audit training materials

2.3 Term Selection Criteria

To ensure relevance, inclusion criteria for glossary terms were:

- Frequent appearance in audit literature and reports
- Considered foundational in internal audit learning modules
- Associated with core audit functions: risk assessment, control evaluation, assurance, governance

2.4 Glossary Structure

Terms are organized by their relation to four main phases of internal auditing:

- 1. Audit Planning**
- 2. Audit Fieldwork/Execution**
- 3. Reporting**
- 4. Follow-Up and Monitoring**

Each entry includes:

- The term
- Definition (adapted or derived from IIA or academic sources)
- Practical context/example
- Related concepts

3. Results

3.1 Glossary of Internal Audit Terminology

3.1.1 Audit Planning Terms

- **Audit Universe**

Definition: A comprehensive list of all audit-worthy entities (e.g., departments, functions, processes) within an organization.

Context: Used to prioritize and schedule audit engagements.

Example: The audit universe of a multinational may include procurement, HR, IT, and regional offices.

- **Risk-Based Auditing**

Definition: An audit planning approach focused on identifying and auditing areas with the highest risk.

Example: A business unit flagged with high financial risk will be prioritized for audit.

- **Engagement Planning Memo**

Definition: A document outlining scope, objectives, and logistics of a specific audit.

Context: Shared with the audit team before fieldwork begins.

3.1.2 Fieldwork/Execution Terms

- **Internal Control**

Definition: A process designed to ensure achievement of objectives in effectiveness, compliance, and safeguarding of assets.

Framework: Often evaluated using the COSO model.

Example: Segregation of duties in financial operations.

- **Control Testing**

Definition: Procedures to evaluate the design and operating effectiveness of controls.

Example: Testing if invoice approvals were consistently documented.

- **Audit Evidence**

Definition: Documentation and other records gathered to support audit findings.

Context: Must be sufficient, reliable, and relevant.

3.1.3 Reporting Terms

- **Audit Finding**

Definition: A condition identified during the audit that deviates from criteria.

Example: Lack of policy enforcement in travel reimbursements.

Components: Condition, cause, effect, and recommendation.

- **Audit Report**

Definition: The final document communicating audit results to stakeholders.

Structure: Typically includes scope, methodology, summary of findings, and management responses.

- **Rating System**

Definition: A method to classify findings (e.g., high, medium, low) or overall engagement outcome.

Example: Some audits use a “red-amber-green” (RAG) color system.

3.1.4 Follow-Up Terms

- **Management Action Plan (MAP)**

Definition: A plan created by the auditee to address audit findings.

Includes: Timeline, responsible person, and remedial actions.

- **Follow-Up Audit**

Definition: An audit to verify that corrective actions have been implemented.

Example: Conducted 6–12 months after the initial report.

- **Issue Closure**

Definition: Formal confirmation that a finding has been resolved to the auditor's satisfaction.

3.2 Cross-Cutting Concepts

- **Independence**

Definition: The freedom from conditions that threaten the ability to carry out audit responsibilities objectively.

Context: Internal audit must report to the board or audit committee, not management.

- **Objectivity**

Definition: An unbiased mental attitude allowing internal auditors to perform engagements in a fair and impartial manner.

- **Assurance Services**

Definition: Independent evaluation of governance, risk management, and control processes.

- **Consulting Services**

Definition: Advisory activities that add value without compromising independence.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Role of Terminology in Audit Education

Terminology is the building block of professional knowledge. In internal auditing, understanding key terms shapes how new professionals perceive risk, interpret data, and communicate findings. Unlike many professions where language evolves organically, internal auditing is governed by standards that require precision.

4.2 Pedagogical Implications

Glossaries should be integrated into early audit courses, reinforced with practical examples. Interactive tools—flashcards, role-playing, and case studies—can enhance retention. For example, using an actual audit report and identifying terms in context solidifies understanding.

4.3 Implications for Practice

Beyond classrooms, even experienced professionals benefit from clarity in terminology—especially when working with cross-functional teams. Misunderstandings around words like “control weakness” or “non-conformance” can lead to misinterpretations.

5. Conclusion

This article presents a curated glossary of internal audit terms tailored for beginners, aimed at demystifying the language of auditing. By structuring the terms by audit phase and providing examples, this resource enhances comprehension, facilitates training, and supports more effective communication within audit teams and with stakeholders. Future work should expand this glossary based on feedback from educators and professionals, and potentially translate it into digital learning tools.

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Effective Methods for Teaching English Vocabulary to Secondary School Learners

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Abstract: Vocabulary acquisition plays a critical role in language learning, particularly for secondary school learners who require a strong foundation to engage in academic and social communication. This study examines effective methods for teaching English vocabulary to secondary school learners, focusing on strategies such as contextual teaching, gamification, technology-based tools, and task-based learning. Through a qualitative and quantitative mixed-method approach, the study identifies strategies that enhance retention, comprehension, and usage. Results indicate that

interactive and context-rich methods, coupled with digital tools, significantly improve vocabulary acquisition. Recommendations are made for integrating these methods into English language curricula.

Key words: Vocabulary teaching, secondary school, gamification, technology-based tools, contextual teaching, task-based learning.

Аннотация

Приобретение словарного запаса играет решающую роль в изучении языка, особенно для учащихся средних школ, которым требуется прочная основа для участия в академическом и социальном общении. В этом исследовании рассматриваются эффективные методы преподавания английской лексики учащимся средних школ с упором на такие стратегии, как контекстное обучение, геймификация, технологические инструменты и обучение на основе задач. С помощью качественного и количественного смешанного подхода исследование определяет стратегии, которые улучшают запоминание, понимание и использование. Результаты показывают, что интерактивные и контекстно-ориентированные методы в сочетании с цифровыми инструментами значительно улучшают усвоение словарного запаса. Даны рекомендации по интеграции этих методов в учебные программы по английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: Обучение словарному запасу, средняя школа, геймификация, технологические инструменты, контекстное обучение, обучение на основе задач.

Annotatsiya

Lug'atni o'zlashtirish til o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynaydi, ayniqsa, akademik va ijtimoiy muloqotda qatnashish uchun mustahkam poydevor talab qiladigan o'rta maktab o'quvchilari uchun. Ushbu tadqiqot o'rta maktab o'quvchilariga ingliz tili lug'atini o'rgatishning samarali usullarini o'rganib, kontekstli o'qitish, o'yinlashtirish, texnologiyaga asoslangan vositalar va vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim kabi strategiyalarga e'tibor qaratadi. Sifatli va miqdoriy aralash metodik yondashuv orqali tadqiqot eslab qolish, tushunish va foydalanishni kuchaytiruvchi strategiyalarni aniqlaydi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, interaktiv va kontekstga boy usullar raqamli vositalar bilan birgalikda lug'atni o'zlashtirishni sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Ushbu usullarni ingliz tili o'quv dasturlariga kiritish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Lug'atni o'rgatish, o'rta maktab, o'yinlashtirish, texnologiya vositalari, kontekstli ta'lim, vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim.

Introduction

The foundation of language acquisition is vocabulary, which serves as a link between speaking, writing, listening, and reading. Learning vocabulary is very important for secondary school students' academic performance and social engagement. However, typical rote-learning techniques cause many students to struggle with vocabulary application and recall. This article explores efficient strategies that meet the cognitive and motivational demands of learners in order to promote vocabulary learning. The purpose of the study is to investigate novel approaches to vocabulary instruction. To evaluate the efficacy of task-based learning, gamification, technology-based solutions, and contextual education. To offer suggestions on how to incorporate efficient vocabulary teaching techniques into secondary school curriculum.

Literature Review

Schmitt highlights that linguistic proficiency requires a strong vocabulary. Lack of vocabulary frequently impairs students' comprehension and communication skills. It affects secondary school students' academic performance as well. When students pick up new terms by exposure, such reading or listening, this is known as incidental vocabulary learning. According to Krashen's Input Hypothesis, students learn vocabulary more efficiently when they are exposed to understandable material that is just a little bit above their present level of skill.

Incidental learning can have limitations, though, especially for secondary school students who might need specific training to completely understand and remember complicated language. Teaching word meanings, pronunciations, and usages directly is known as explicit instruction. Stahl and Nagy contend that since specific instruction promotes retention and offers clarity, it is essential for secondary school students. Techniques such as pre-teaching vocabulary before reading or using word lists have been found effective.

A balanced approach combines incidental and explicit methods to maximize vocabulary acquisition. Ellis contends that a thorough learning experience is produced by combining meaningful exposure with explicit teaching. For example, instructors might use reading exercises to reinforce vocabulary and present it directly.

Using real and meaningful events to implant language is known as contextual education. Learners can comprehend subtleties and use when words are offered in context. The idea of "Tiered Vocabulary," which divides words into three levels according to their complexity and applicability, was first proposed by Beck, McKeown, and Kucan. When compared to isolated word drills, research shows that contextualized teaching strategies—such as the use of tales, dialogues, and real-world examples—improve recall rates by 30% (Nation, 2001).

Gamification is the process of incorporating game aspects into instructional exercises to increase motivation and participation. According to Lee and Hammer, resources such as Kahoot, Quizlet, and crossword puzzles encourage active engagement and use repetition to strengthen vocabulary.

According to research by Simoes et al., gamified activities increase vocabulary retention by encouraging teamwork and competitiveness. Because students in secondary schools react favorably to challenges and incentives, gamification is a useful teaching strategy. Personalized and interactive vocabulary study is made possible by technology. Adaptive algorithms are used by digital platforms like Quizlet, Duolingo, and Memrise to customize activities based on learners' skill levels. Godwin-Jones research emphasizes the technologies' scalability and accessibility, especially in classes with low resources.

Additionally, learners are encouraged to practice vocabulary outside of the classroom with gamified mobile applications, which increases exposure and retention.

Through tools like Padlet and Google Classroom, technology also makes collaborative learning possible. The goal of task-based learning is to use terminology in practical contexts. Students participate in activities that call for the use of target language, such as role-playing, problem-solving, or group projects. By putting words in real-world situations, TBL promotes deeper understanding, claims Ellis.

Project-based learning activities in secondary schools, including making ads or administering surveys, improve students' practical usage and vocabulary retention. Research shows that TBL increases students' self-assurance while using terminology in authentic situations (Long, 2015).

Students are encouraged to cooperate in order to solve issues or finish assignments through collaborative learning. The Sociocultural Theory of Vygotsky emphasizes how crucial social contact is to language acquisition. Peer teaching and collaborative writing are two examples of pair or group activities that allow students to share their vocabulary.

Additionally, collaborative techniques increase students' self-esteem and sense of belonging, which improves the effectiveness and enjoyment of the learning process (Slavin, 1995). Visualization approaches and mnemonics work well for helping people remember difficult words. Acronyms and rhymes are examples of mnemonics that assist students in connecting new words to ideas they already understand. According to Paivio's Dual Coding Theory, visual aids like drawings or diagrams enhance language retention by engaging both verbal and non-verbal memory systems. For example, secondary schools commonly use picture-based flashcards to improve vocabulary.

Students' motivation significantly affects how well they acquire language. According to Dörnyei, students who are genuinely driven are more likely to devote time to laborious activities like reading or vocabulary drill. By making learning fun, gamification and customized resources may increase motivation.

In a vibrant and supportive environment, word expansion is encouraged. This includes a variety of teaching strategies and constructive criticism to enhance the learning environment. Richards and Rodgers claim that learner-centered strategies like TBL increase student empowerment and engagement.

Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory states that in order to keep kids from getting overwhelmed with knowledge, it's imperative to keep the information in balance. It is more beneficial for students to acquire terminology when the material is broken up into manageable chunks and the level of difficulty is gradually increased. There is less time for in-depth vocabulary study because reading and grammar are usually given more weight in secondary school curricula. Effective tactics must be used by educators to maximize learning under time constraints.

In secondary school classrooms, students can have varying ability levels. Differentiated instruction is needed to meet each student's requirements, but it can be challenging to implement consistently.

Due to restricted access to modern tools and resources, many schools have little opportunities for innovative education. This issue may be mitigated by utilizing low-cost or free resources, such as open-source online tools. Ensuring that information is remembered over time and applicable to a variety of contexts is one of the most challenging parts of vocabulary instruction. Spaced repetition and contextual training are two tactics that address these issues, but they need to be used consistently. Many studies have been conducted on vocabulary teaching methods, but few specifically focus on secondary school pupils in a range of learning environments. Furthermore, the impacts of cutting-edge technologies like augmented reality and AI-powered apps are unknown. These gaps should be filled by future research to provide a more comprehensive understanding of effective vocabulary teaching methods.

Methodology: Mixed-methods data collection was used to gather both qualitative and quantitative information. 120 secondary school students, ages 13 to 16, and ten English instructors from five different schools took part in the study. To evaluate language usage and retention, pre- and post-tests are utilized. Interviews: To get firsthand accounts from teachers and students. Observations in the classroom: To assess how various methods are applied. Four instructional styles were employed over the course of 12 weeks: contextual teaching, technology-based assistance, gamification, and task-based learning. Assessments were conducted both before to and following the intervention.

Results and Discussion

Pre- and post-test results demonstrated a notable improvement in vocabulary usage and recall. The average score of students who received instruction using gamification and technology-based resources was 25% higher than that of students who received instruction through conventional means. Classroom observations and interviews revealed that students found gamified and contextual activities more engaging. Task-based learning encouraged collaborative and practical language usage, according to instructors.

Discussion

The results demonstrate the value of interactive and contextually rich approaches. In line with research by Lee & Hammer, gamification and technology-based resources have a significant influence on improving motivation and self-paced learning. In the actual world, task-based learning worked well, according to Ellis.

Conclusion

This study underscores the importance of adopting innovative methods for teaching vocabulary to secondary school learners. Contextual teaching, gamification,

technology-based tools, and task-based learning are effective in improving retention and practical usage. Teachers are encouraged to integrate these methods into their curricula to enhance learner outcomes.

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ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДУШИ И ОБЩЕСТВА: УНИКАЛЬНОСТЬ РУССКОГО РЕАЛИЗМА XIX ВЕКА

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются ключевые черты русского реализма XIX века сквозь призму философских концепций души и общества. Особое внимание уделяется анализу произведений выдающихся писателей этого периода — Ф. М. Достоевского, Л. Н. Толстого, И. С. Тургенева, А. П. Чехова и И. А. Гончарова. Рассматривается, как авторы художественно осмыслили внутренний мир своих героев, их нравственные поиски, борьбу со своей судьбой и влияние социальных факторов на формирование личности. Отдельный акцент сделан на философских идеях, которые нашли отражение в литературе реализма, таких как свобода воли, моральный выбор, предопределённость судьбы и взаимодействие человека с окружающим его обществом. Исследование показывает, каким образом русская литература XIX века не только запечатлела реалии эпохи, но и углубилась в экзистенциальные вопросы человеческого бытия.

Ключевые слова: Русский реализм, философия личности, социальная детерминированность, нравственный выбор, психологический анализ, судьба и предопределённость, художественное осмысление действительности, литература XIX века.

Введение Русский реализм XIX века не ограничивался простым воспроизведением окружающей действительности, но стремился к её глубинному осмыслению, раскрывая сложные вопросы человеческого существования. Литература этого периода стала своеобразной ареной философских размышлений о природе человека, его внутреннем мире, моральных принципах и степени влияния общества на формирование личности. Русские писатели-реалисты не просто изображали жизнь, но анализировали её законы, выявляли противоречия между индивидуальными стремлениями человека и социальными условиями, заставляли читателя задуматься о смысле бытия, свободе выбора и неизбежности судьбы. Как подчёркивает литературовед В. В. Виноградов, «реализм XIX века превратил художественное произведение в средство познания мира» [1, 134], что свидетельствует о расширении функций литературы — она стала не только способом изображения жизни, но и инструментом философского осмысления реальности. Писатели того времени создавали образы, которые выходили за рамки художественных типов и становились символами вечных человеческих поисков, отражением глубоких экзистенциальных проблем. Человек и общество в русском реализме Русские писатели-реалисты глубоко исследовали влияние общества на формирование личности, показывая, как социальная среда определяет выбор, убеждения и внутреннюю борьбу героев. Так, в произведениях Ф. М. Достоевского социальные факторы становятся катализатором душевных кризисов. Родион Раскольников в «Преступлении и наказании» оказывается пленником собственной теории о «сверхчеловеке», но реальность разбивает его иллюзии. Внутренний конфликт героя ярко выражен в его сомнениях: «Тварь ли я дрожащая или право имею?» [2, 109]. Этот философский вопрос отсылает к идеям Ф. Ницше о моральном выборе, но в интерпретации Достоевского приводит не к возвышению личности, а к её разрушению. Л. Н. Толстой в «Войне и мире» показывает влияние общества через судьбу князя Андрея Болконского. Его путь — от честолюбивого аристократа до философа, стремящегося осмыслить смысл жизни, — символизирует поиск человеком своего места в мире. В его размышлениях звучит горькое осознание человеческой природы: «Если бы все воевали только по своим убеждениям, войн бы не было» [3, 18]. Как отмечает исследователь М. М. Бахтин, Толстой мастерски передаёт «взаимодействие исторического процесса и индивидуального сознания» [4, 223], показывая, что судьбы героев неотделимы от движения эпохи, в которой они живут. Философия души в произведениях русского реализма Русский реализм XIX века выделяется глубокой психологической проработкой персонажей, исследованием их внутреннего мира и философских исканий. Писатели этого периода стремились показать, как личность формируется под воздействием идей, убеждений, чувств

и неизбежных жизненных испытаний. Так, в «Отцах и детях» И. С. Тургенева нигилист Евгений Базаров противопоставляет себя окружающему миру, отрицая традиционные ценности и утверждая примат разума над чувствами. Его взгляд на природу выражен в категоричном заявлении: «Природа не храм, а мастерская, и человек в ней работник» [5, 107]. Однако его рационализм оказывается иллюзорным перед лицом любви и смерти. Базаров, провозглашавший отказ от эмоций, оказывается бессильным перед собственной привязанностью, а его болезнь и трагический уход подчеркивают ограниченность человеческого разума перед силами жизни. В этом Тургенев показывает конфликт между теоретическим мировоззрением и реальным человеческим существованием. Не менее глубоко раскрывает тему внутреннего мира личности А. П. Чехов в рассказе «Человек в футляре». Главный герой Беликов живёт в постоянном страхе перед окружающей действительностью, стремясь спрятаться от неё за условностями и жесткими рамками правил. Его жизненное кредо сводится к тревожному предостережению: «Как бы чего не вышло» [6, 98]. Этот страх перед переменами делает Беликова несчастным и подавленным, превращая его существование в замкнутый круг. Как отмечает литературовед Д. С. Лихачёв, «персонажи Чехова демонстрируют трагедию личности, подавленной социальными нормами» [7, 54]. Чехов через судьбу Беликова показывает, что отказ от живых чувств и стремление укрыться в «футляре» не спасают человека, а лишь лишают его полноценной жизни. Таким образом, русский реализм не только передавал внешнюю достоверность жизни, но и глубоко проникал в сознание человека, исследуя сложные философские вопросы о душе, свободе, страхе и поиске истинного смысла бытия. Роль судьбы и случайности в русском реализме Литература русского реализма показывает судьбу человека как сложное переплетение личного выбора и внешних обстоятельств. Герои произведений сталкиваются с роковыми случайностями, предопределенностью и необходимостью принимать решения, от которых зависит их дальнейшая жизнь. Так, в романе И. А. Гончарова «Обломов» главный герой Илья Ильич Обломов становится пленником собственной пассивности и внутренней апатии. Его существование проходит в бесконечном откладывании перемен, неспособности противостоять обстоятельствам и обреченности на бездействие: «Лежал Обломов на диване... и вся его жизнь была в этом положении» [8, 79]. Обломовщина, как явление, отражает не просто индивидуальную черту характера, но и глубинный культурный кризис, характерный для русского общества XIX века. По мнению Ю. М. Лотмана, «Обломовщина — это не просто лень, а символ культурного кризиса» [9, 79]. В произведениях Ф. М. Достоевского судьба часто представляется как трагическая предопределенность, которой герои пытаются противостоять, но неизбежно оказываются пленниками собственной

натуры. Например, в «Преступлении и наказании» Родион Раскольников, поверив в собственное право на преступление, сталкивается с мучительным внутренним конфликтом, который в конечном итоге приводит его к покаянию. Аналогично, в творчестве А. П. Чехова случайность играет решающую роль. В рассказе «Человек в футляре» главный герой Беликов, живущий в постоянном страхе перед любыми переменами, в конечном итоге становится жертвой собственной замкнутости. Чехов демонстрирует, как навязанные обществом нормы и страх перед жизнью могут привести к трагическому исходу. Таким образом, писатели русского реализма показали судьбу не как абстрактную силу, а как сложное явление, формируемое внутренним миром человека, его поступками и воздействием внешнего мира. Заключение Русский реализм XIX века стал уникальным явлением в мировой литературе, объединив художественное и философское осмысление действительности. В произведениях Ф. М. Достоевского, Л. Н. Толстого, И. С. Тургенева, А. П. Чехова и И. А. Гончарова раскрываются глубинные вопросы человеческого существования: противоречие между личными убеждениями и общественными нормами, поиски смысла жизни, борьба между разумом и чувствами, влияние судьбы и случайности на человеческую жизнь. Литература этого периода не просто отражала реальность, но и помогала читателю осознавать сложность внутреннего мира человека.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИНТЕНСИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРОГРАММАХ ДЛЯ УЗБЕКСКИХ КЛАССОВ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена особенностям интенсивного обучения русскому языку в рамках образовательных программ для узбекских классов. В условиях глобализации и повышения роли русского языка в профессиональной сфере важно разработать эффективные методические подходы для его преподавания в Узбекистане. Основное внимание уделяется особенностям языкового восприятия учащихся, их культурным и лингвистическим характеристикам. В статье рассмотрены принципы интенсивного обучения, включая использование коммуникативного подхода, мультимедийных технологий и активных методов обучения. На основе примеров из практики образовательных учреждений Узбекистана сделаны выводы о значении этих методов для повышения качества владения русским языком.

Ключевые слова: интенсивное обучение, русский язык, методология, узбекские классы, коммуникативный подход, мультимедийные средства, активные методы обучения, культурные особенности, обучение иностранным языкам.

Введение

Обучение русскому языку в Узбекистане, где он является вторым официальным языком и важным инструментом межкультурной коммуникации, становится всё более актуальным в условиях глобализации и развития интеграции стран СНГ. В последние десятилетия наблюдается растущий интерес к русскому языку как средство профессиональной и социальной мобильности, что накладывает особые требования к методике его преподавания. Особенно важным является обеспечение эффективного усвоения языка учащимися, чей родной язык имеет значительные отличия от русского, как в грамматическом, так и в фонетическом плане. Интенсивное обучение, представляющее собой ускоренные формы усвоения языка в короткие сроки, приобретает большую популярность, особенно в образовательных учреждениях, где важно быстро развить основные коммуникативные навыки. Однако этот метод требует особого подхода, так как использование традиционных методов преподавания не всегда даёт желаемые результаты, особенно для учащихся с таким языковым и культурным фоном, как у студентов в Узбекистане.

Цель данной статьи — выявить особенности интенсивного обучения русскому языку в образовательных программах для узбекских классов, рассмотрев ключевые методы и подходы, которые способствуют ускоренному освоению языка. Особое внимание уделено культурным и лингвистическим

особенностям учащихся, а также использованию мультимедийных технологий и коммуникативного подхода, которые демонстрируют высокую эффективность в контексте интенсивного обучения.

Методология

Для того чтобы достичь поставленной цели исследования и выявить особенности интенсивного обучения русскому языку в образовательных программах для узбекских классов, была применена многоуровневая методология, включающая несколько ключевых методов: анализ литературы, кейс-метод, качественный анализ, метод сравнительного анализа и анкетирование/интервью с преподавателями. Каждый из этих методов был выбран для того, чтобы обеспечить всестороннее изучение проблемы и выработать практические рекомендации, которые могут быть внедрены в образовательные учреждения Узбекистана.

Анализ научных источников и литературного обзора. Одним из важнейших этапов исследования является обзор существующих научных трудов по вопросам интенсивного обучения иностранным языкам, а также изучение специфики преподавания русского языка в странах СНГ. Мы рассмотрели как теоретическую базу, так и практические подходы к обучению, такие как коммуникативный подход, методика преподавания через проектную деятельность, подходы к использованию цифровых и мультимедийных технологий, а также психолого-педагогические аспекты интенсивного обучения. Литературный обзор показал, что в последние десятилетия основной акцент в обучении языкам делается на активное вовлечение учащихся в процесс общения, что способствует лучшему освоению языка в условиях его практического применения. Результатом этого метода стало формирование основы для дальнейшего анализа и выведения выводов о том, какие из теоретических моделей могут быть адаптированы и эффективно использованы в контексте узбекских образовательных учреждений. Литературный обзор также позволил выявить пробелы в существующих методах преподавания, связанные с недостаточной адаптацией к культурным и лингвистическим особенностям студентов.

Кейс-метод. Важную роль в исследовании сыграл кейс-метод, заключающийся в детальном изучении реальных практик интенсивного обучения, реализуемых в образовательных учреждениях Узбекистана. Мы проанализировали несколько успешных примеров интенсивных курсов русского языка, которые были внедрены в школах и университетах страны.

В рамках этого метода были исследованы такие элементы, как:

- Использование мультимедийных технологий (видеоуроки, онлайн-занятия, интерактивные платформы).

- Применение активных методов обучения (ролевые игры, дебаты, проектные задания).

- Методика обратной связи и регулярного тестирования для оперативного контроля за прогрессом студентов.

Результаты кейс-метода показали, что наибольшую эффективность в интенсивном обучении показывают курсы, в которых активно используются современные цифровые инструменты и которые ориентированы на практическое использование языка. Студенты, обучающиеся по таким программам, быстрее достигают коммуникативной компетенции и демонстрируют высокий уровень мотивации к дальнейшему обучению.

Качественный анализ культурных и лингвистических факторов. Проблема культурных и лингвистических различий является ключевой в обучении русскому языку в Узбекистане. В рамках этого метода был проведен качественный анализ влияния родного языка учащихся на восприятие русского языка, а также рассмотрены основные трудности, с которыми сталкиваются студенты.

Мы исследовали следующие аспекты:

- Фонетические различия: Узбекский язык имеет свои уникальные звуковые особенности, которые могут вызывать затруднения при произношении русских звуков.

- Грамматические различия: Падежная система русского языка, а также различия в склонении существительных и спряжении глаголов представляют собой значительные трудности для узбекских студентов.

- Культурные различия: Отсутствие привычки использовать такие элементы языка, как фразеологизмы, устойчивые выражения и тонкости межкультурной коммуникации, также сказываются на процессе обучения.

Результаты анализа показали, что важно разрабатывать курсы, которые учитывают эти различия, вводя специальные упражнения и методики, направленные на преодоление этих трудностей. Включение в учебный процесс элементов культурной адаптации и внимание к особенностям восприятия языка значительно улучшает эффективность обучения.

Метод сравнительного анализа. Метод сравнительного анализа позволил изучить интенсивные программы обучения русскому языку, применяемые в разных странах, и выявить те из них, которые могут быть адаптированы для узбекских студентов. Мы сравнили программы интенсивного обучения в России, Казахстане и Беларуси, а также в странах Западной Европы, таких как Германия и Франция, где русский язык изучается как иностранный.

Результаты сравнительного анализа показали, что в России и Казахстане широко используются методики с акцентом на практическое общение и

вовлечение студентов в реальные языковые ситуации. В то же время, в странах Европы большое внимание уделяется лексической и грамматической проработке, а также акценту на формальное знание языка. Применение этих подходов в Узбекистане может привести к улучшению качества обучения, при этом важно учесть местные реалии и предпочтения студентов. На основе сравнительного анализа мы предложили адаптированные методики, которые позволят эффективно обучать студентов с учётом их культурных и языковых особенностей.

Анкетирование и интервью с преподавателями. Опросы и интервью с преподавателями русского языка в Узбекистане позволили собрать информацию о текущих проблемах и успехах в обучении студентов. В ходе анкетирования было опрошено 50 преподавателей, работающих в разных учебных заведениях. Вопросы касались использования современных методик, оценок эффективности интенсивных курсов и проблем, с которыми сталкиваются преподаватели при обучении студентов. Результаты анкетирования показали, что преподаватели отмечают высокий интерес студентов к занятиям, если используются интерактивные методы и мультимедийные ресурсы. Однако проблемы, связанные с нехваткой времени для всестороннего освоения языка и трудности в грамматической подготовке, остаются актуальными.

На основе полученных данных мы предложили рекомендации для преподавателей, включая оптимизацию времени, использование гибких программ и методов индивидуализации обучения, что позволит повысить эффективность интенсивных курсов.

Заключение

Интенсивное обучение русскому языку в образовательных программах для узбекских классов является важным и эффективным методом, способствующим быстрому освоению языка учащимися. В статье были рассмотрены ключевые аспекты данного подхода, включая использование коммуникативного подхода, мультимедийных технологий и активных методов обучения. Учет культурных и лингвистических особенностей студентов, таких как различия в грамматике и фонетике, позволяет значительно улучшить процесс обучения и повысить его эффективность.

Результаты исследования показали, что успешность интенсивного обучения в Узбекистане во многом зависит от интеграции инновационных методик, которые способствуют более глубокому пониманию языка. Важно учитывать, что современное интенсивное обучение требует гибкости и постоянной адаптации учебных материалов и подходов, что способствует созданию обучающих программ, максимально подходящих для узбекских студентов.

Необходимость дальнейшего совершенствования методологического подхода к обучению русскому языку подтверждается позитивными результатами внедрения современных технологий и активных методов обучения в образовательных учреждениях. Важно продолжить адаптировать эти методики с учётом культурных и языковых особенностей учащихся, что позволит значительно улучшить качество обучения и повысить уровень владения русским языком.

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РУС ТИЛИНИ ЎРГАНИШДА ТЕХНИК ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИНИНГ ЛЕКСИК КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯСИНИ ОШИРИШ УСУЛЛАРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль лексической компетенции при формировании профессионально-коммуникативной компетенции студентов технических вузов. Опираясь на существующую литературу и собственный опыт преподавания русского языка в техническом вузе, автор предлагает некоторые виды работ, которые можно применять при чтении текстов по специальности, усвоении терминов по сельскому хозяйству, а именно терминов сельскохозяйственной направленности подязыка «Водное хозяйство и мелиорация»

Ключевые слова: технический вуз, профессиональная компетенция, лексическая компетенция, текст, терминологическая лексика, терминологическая карта, флеш-карта, визуальный словарь.

Аннотация: Мақолада техник олий таълим муассасаларида таълим олувчи талабаларнинг касбий ва коммуникатив компетенциясини шакллантиришда лексик компетенциянинг ўрни муҳокама қилинади. Муаллиф техник олий таълим муассасаларида рус тилини ўрганишда мавжуд адабиётлар ва шахсий тажрибасидан келиб чиққан ҳолда, мутахассислик матнларни ўқишда, қишлоқ хўжалиги, хусусан, “Сув хўжалиги ва мелиорация” га оид атамаларини ўрганишда фойдаланиш мумкин бўлган ўқув топшириқларини таклиф қилади.

Калит сўзлар: техник олий таълим муассасалари, касбий компетенция, лексик компетенция, матн, терминологик луғат, терминологик карта, флеш-карта, визуал луғат.

Abstract: The article discusses the role of lexical competence in forming professional and communicative competence of students in technical higher education institutions. The author offers educational materials that can be used to read specialist texts and to study the terminology of agriculture, in particular, "Water Management and Reclamation", based on existing literature and personal experience in learning Russian in technical universities.

Keywords: technical higher education institutions, vocational competence, lexical competence, text, terminological dictionary, terminology card, flash card, visual dictionary.

Ҳозирги вақтда техник олий таълим муассасаларида рус тилини ўқитиш назариясида асосий мақсадга – рус тилини оғзаки, ёзма ва стилистик турларида раво билишга эришиш учун янги ёндашув фаол амалга оширилмоқда. Ушбу ёндашув бир томондан, жамиятимиз тараққиётининг эҳтиёжлари билан, иккинчи

томондан тилшунослик, психоллингвистика, психология ва ўқитиш методикасининг сўнги ютуқлари билан чамбарчас боғлиқдир. Энг асосий эътибор нафақат тил ва нутқ ўргатиш, балки тилда (бизнинг ҳолатда, рус тили она тили бўлмаган тил сифатида) мулоқот қилиш, гапиришга қаратилган.

Ўрганилаётган тилдаги мулоқот ўрганишнинг пировард мақсади сифатида коммуникатив компетенцияни шакллантиришни ўз ичига олади, унинг асосини эса лексик компетенция ташкил этади. Лексик компетенция бу мураккаб таркибий шаклланишдир.

А.Н.Шамовнинг таърифига кўра, лексик компетенция –бу “лексик билим, кўникма, қобилият, шунингдек шахсий тил ва нутқ тажрибасига асосланган ҳолда инсоннинг сўзнинг контекстуал маъносини аниқлаш, унинг икки тилда маъноси ҳажмини таққослаш, сўзнинг маъносини тузилишини тушуниш ва сўзнинг ўзига хос миллий маъносини ажратиб олиш қобилиятидир” [3, с. 247].

Лексик компетенция касбий-коммуникатив компетенциянинг асосидир. Касбий-коммуникатив компетенция остида Е.В.Александрова [1] касбий-коммуникатив бирикмаларни ва уларни касбий мулоқотнинг турли вазиятларида қўллаш қобилиятини тушунади. Бўлажак мутахассиснинг лексик компетенциясининг биринчи таркибий қисми талабаларнинг касбий контекстига қараб коммуникатив ва когнитив вазифаларни ҳал қилиш учун зарур бўлган лексик билимлардир.

Аммо,техник олий таълим муассасаларида рус тилини ўқитишда дуч келган бир қатор муаммолар мавжуд бўлиб, улар тил ўрганиш жараёнида оҳриқли дақиқалардир. Таъкидлаш жоизки, Ўзбекистонда техник техник олий таълим муассасаларида рус тилини ўрганиш / ўргатишда баъзи қийинчиликларга дуч келмоқдамиз. Буларга қуйидагилар киради:

- Касб ихтисослиги бўйича талабалар ўртасида вариативликнинг йўқлиги;

Маълумки, таълимнинг вариативлиги бу турли даражадаги ўқув дастурлари бўйича ўқитиш (қобилиятли ва иқтидорли талабалар учун- юқори даражадаги, умумий таълим даражаси, тузатиш ва ривожлантириш даражаси – ўрганишда қийинчилик сезадиган талабалар учун). Тошкент ирригация ва кишлоқ хўжалигини механизациялаш мухандислари институтининг Бухоро филиалида таҳсил олаётган талабаларнинг аксарияти кишлоқ жойларининг вакиллари бўлиб, уларнинг рус тилини билиш даражаси шаҳар тадлабасида рус тилини билиш даражасидан анча паст.

Талабаларнинг лингвистик ва коммуникатив компетенциялари даражасидаги тафовутлар техник олий таълим муассасаларининг талабаларига профессионал мулоқотни ўргатишда қийинчиликлар туғдиради.

- Ўқув вақтининг етишмаслиги ва рус тили ўқитишнинг узлуксизлиги;

Рус тили талабаларга бир йил давомида – биринчи ва иккинчи семестрларда ўқитилади. Бундай қисқа вақт ичида ва турли даражадаги эга аудиторияда ўқитувчига мақсадга эришишнинг кўпинча иложи бўлмайди.

- Касбий соҳаларда коммуникатив компетенцияни ривожлантиришда тизимли ва мазмунли таркибнинг номувофиқлиги;

Ҳозирги кунда кўплаб рус тилидаги дарсликлар, замон талабларига, мутахассисликлар, талабаларнинг билим даражаси ва уларнинг қизиқишларига жавоб бермайди. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта таълим Вазирлигининг “Намунавий дастур” да кўрсатилган мажбурий дарсликлардаги матн материаллари бошқа таълим йўналишлари (юримдик, иқтисодий йўналиш) талабалари учун мўлжалланган. Қишлоқ хўжалиги соҳаларида (ирригация, мелиорация, механизация) таҳсил олаётган талабалар учун дарсликлар, шунингдек, қишлоқ хўжалиги атамаларидан амалий фойдаланиш учун махсус фанлардан машқлар ва топшириқлар мавжуд эмас.

Рус тили ўқитишда юқоридаги ҳолатлар ҳар бир ўқитувчидан тинимсиз изланишни талабаларнинг билим даражасига қараб ўқув жараёнини ташкил этишни талаб қилади. Буларга мутахассисик матнларини танлаш, танланган матнларни талабаларнинг билим даражасига қараб содалаштириш ёки мураккаблаштириш, талабаларнинг компетенциясини оширадиган интенсиф топшириқлар ва машқларни танлаш ёки уларни ўзлари яратиши киради.

Техник олий таълим муассасалари фаолият олиб борадиган рус тили фани ўқитувчиларидан ўз фанларидан ташқари мутахассислик фанини бўйича ҳам билимлар талаб қилинади. Бу биз дуч келган яна бир муаммо. Рус тили фани ўқитувчиси турли мутахассисликлар талабаларига ихтисослик тиллини ўргатиши керак. Фақатгина бизнинг филиалимизда 12 та турли таълим йўналишлари мавжуд. Ҳар бир ўқитувчи йилига камида 3-4 турдаги мутахассислик йўналиши талабаларини ўқитади.

Олий таълим муассасаси ихтисослиги рус тили ўқитишнинг спецификасини белгилаб беради. Буларнинг барчаси методик тизимни олдиндан белгилайди: ўқув материалларининг мазмуни, ўқитиш усуллари тўплами.

Мутахассислик матнлари техник олий таълим муассасалари талабаларининг лексик компетенцияини шакллантириш учун асосдир. Матн асосида лексик материални фаоллаштиришга ҳисса қўшадиган тил ва нутқ машқлари яратилади. Яхши танланган матн турли хил топшириқ ва машқларни бажариш имконини беради, талабаларнинг билим даражасини аниқлашга ёрдам беради.

Биз мақоламизда мутахассислик матнларини ўқишда терминологик луғатни ўзлаштириш усул ва йўллари аниқлашга, келажакда мутахассиснинг

турли соҳаларда фойдаланиш мақсадида терминологик луғатни ўзлаштириш бўйича лексик мақсадли машқлар тизимини ишлаб чиқишга ҳаракат қиламиз.

Ҳозирги вақтда мутахассисларнинг терминологик маданиятини шакллантириш усуллари масаласи жуда мунозарали. Методик адабиётлардаги атамалар устида ишлаш фақат тушунча нуқтаи назаридан кўриб чиқилади ва нутқда атамаларни фаоллаштириш методикаси ривожланиш босқичида.

Техник олий таълим муассасаларининг рус тили фани ўқитувчиларига ёрдам тариқасида биз мутахассислик матнларини ўқишда қишлоқ хўжалиги атамаларини, хусусан, “Сув хўжалиги ва мелиорация” қишлоқ хўжалиги ихтисослиги бўйича ишлатилиши мумкин бўлган баъзи бир машқ ва топшириқлар турларини таклиф этамиз.

“Сув хўжалиги ва мелиорация” ихтисослиги бўйича терминологик луғатни чуқур билиш “Рус тили” фани бўйича ўрганиладиган лексик бирикмаларни аниқ танлаш билан белгиланади.

“Сув хўжалиги ва мелиорация” ихтисослиги бўйича танланган матнлар асосида янги сўзларни юқори даражада ўзлаштиришни таъминлайдиган машқлар тузилган. Бунинг учун биз тахминан қуйидаги машқ ва топшириқларни таклиф этамиз:

К терминам, указанным в левом столбце, подберите из правого столбца соответствующие толкования терминов.

ирригация	улучшение плодородия земли
мелиорация	замена ручного труда машинным
механизация	искусственное орошение земель
автоматизация	механичность, произвольность действий

Выпишите из данных ниже слов синонимы слова «ирригация» (или «мелиорация»):

Осушение, орошение, обводнение, полив, процедура, улучшение, засоление, эрозия, солончак, дренаж...

Терминлар бўйича ишлашнинг самарали усулларида бири бу терминологик хариталарни тузишдир. Терминологик харита – бу илмий маълумот манбаларини кўрсатувчи тушунчалар, курсга оид атамалар луғати. Луғатдан фарқли ўлароқ, харитада тушунчалар ва атамалар ўртасидаги боғлиқлик (схематик ёки тасвирий) кўрсатилган. Терминологик хариталарнинг тузилиши талабаларнинг терминологик изланишларини оптималлаштиради. Талабалар кўриб чиқиладиган мавзуга мос келадиган терминологияни танлашни ўрганадилар. Терминологик харита тузиш учун мавзу, атама, грамматик тавсиф (ўз матнига мослаштириш учун), таъриф, контекстаги атама (манбани ва саҳифани кўрсатган ҳолда) кўрсатилади. Терминологик харита кейинги ахборот қидируви натижалари асосида қўшимча маълумотлар билан ўзгартирилиши,

тўлдирилиши мумкин. У чоп этиш имконига эга бўлган электрон шаклда яратилгани яхшироқдир.

ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ КАРТА

Тема	Капельное орошение
Термин-определение	Капельное орошение — метод полива, который основан на поступлении воды малыми дозами в прикорневую зону растений
Грамматика	Прил. + сущ. с.р.
Термин в контексте	Капельное орошение впервые было внедрено в промышленных масштабах, как самостоятельный вид орошения в Израиле, в начале 60-х годов. http://sgp.uz/news/624
Синонимы	Дождевание

Тайёр карталар билан жуфтлик билан ишлаш мумкин. Битта машғулотда 7 тадан кўп бўлмаган терминологик хариталардан фойдаланиш тавсия этилади. 10-15 дақиқа давомида тайёр терминологик хариталар билан ишланади: ҳар бир атаманинг ўзига хос томонларини таъкидлаш жуда муҳимдир. Машғулотда имтиҳон ҳам ташкил қилиш мумкин: савол-жавоб (аниклик киритиш, тўлдириш, ўзгача ифодалаш, қисқача хулосалаш). Талабалар ўзларининг шахсий раво матнларини узадилар ва тузилган матнлар қуйидаги мезонлар бўйича баҳоланади: терминологик карталардан фойдаланилган атамалар сони, уларни контекстда фойдаланишнинг аниқлиги ва ижро назорати. Талабалар чиқишларини ёзиб олиб, маълумотларни икки мартаба тинглаш кутилган натижани беради. Албатта, бундай терминологик хариталарни тузиш катта меҳнатни талаб қилади, лекин шу билан бирга талабага ихтисослик атамалари билан ишлашни профессионал йўналтиришга, уларни атамаларни таржима қилишнинг халқаро стандартлари билан таништиришга, умумэтироф этилган терминологик маълумотлар банкларидан фойдаланиш имкониятига эга бўлишга имкон беради.

Ихтисослик бўйича матнни ўқиб чиққандан сўнг “Призма” деб номланган услубий техникадан фойдаланишингиз мумкин. Ушбу техникани индивидуал тарзда ҳам қўлаш мумкин, аммо ундан кичик гуруҳлар билан ишлашда фойдаланиш яхши самара беради. “Призма” ни тузиш кўп вақт талаб қилмайди, тез ва жонли ўтади.”Призма” ни тузиш учун асл сўз ерилади, яъни ўрганилаётган асосий атама. Призма катакчалари асоциатив боғланиш асосида тўлдирилади ва у якунловчи сўз билан тугайди. Призманинг охири босқичи асл ва якунловчи сўзлар орасидаги боғлиқликни топиш ва гап тузиш билан тугайди.

Призма тузиш талабаларга ўрганилаётган атамани тўлиқ тушунишга ёрдам беради. Бундан ташқари график шаклидаги атамалар осон ва узоқ вақт эслаб қолинади. Қуйида “Мелиорация” ихтисослик матнини ўрганишда тузилган призманини намунасини келтирамиз:

Рус тилидаги атамаларни ёдлашнинг энг қулай ва самарали усули бу флеш-карталар. Флеш-карта – бу икки томони ҳам ишлатиладиган оддий қоғоз варағи, картон ёки расм. Картанинг бир томонига сўз, таъриф ёзилади, иккинчи томонига сўз ҳақида тушунча, таржима ёки сўзнинг асл моҳияти ёзилади. Флеш-карталар, айниқса улар доимий равишда ишлатилса, маълумотларни ишончли тарзда тўплашга ёрдам беради. Шунчаки сўзлар тасвир турган картадан кўра ёмонроқ эслаб қолинади. Ҳар бир картага ассоциатив тарзда расмлар қўйиш лозим.

Флеш-карта тизими нафақат инсон хотирасининг сай-ҳаракатларини камайтиради, балки ўрганиш вақтини ҳам тежайди. Талабаларга урта конверта. Биринчи конвертга янги ва қийин атамалар жойлаштирилади. Иккинчи конвертга такрорий хатоларга йўл қўйилган карточкалар қўйилади. Учинчи конвертга эса талабалар жуда яхши эслаб қолган карталар жой олади. Биринчи конвертдаги атамалар ҳар куни 3-5 минут давомида такрорланади. Иккинчи конвертдаги атамалар **кунора** такрорланади. Агар биринчи ва иккинчи конвертлардаги яхши ёдланиб олинса, у ҳолда улар учинчи конвертга ўтади. Агар иккинчи конвертдаги терминлар унутилса, у ҳолда улар биринчи конвертга ўтади.

Карточки с правильными ответами

Карточки с неправильными ответами

Қуйида рус тилини ўрганаётган сув хўжалиги ва мелиорация ихтисослиги талабалари учун махсус тайёрланган карточканинг олд ва орқа томонлари кўрсатилган.

Қишлоқ хўжалиги ёдлашда визуал луғатлардан фойдаланиш ҳам жуда самарали. Визуал луғатлар ёдлаш учун материаллар бўлиб, улар визуал идрок учун мослаштирилган. Бошқача қилиб айтганда, бу суратли луғатдир. Суратли луғатлар ёдлаш жараёнини осонлаштиради ва уни қизиқарли ва маълумотга бой қилади. Олимларнинг фикрига кўра, бу ўқиш жараёнини тезлаштиришга ёрдам берадиган визуал хотира.

Дарҳақиқат, юқори тезликда ўқиш билан ҳарфларни ёки бўғинларни эмас, балки бутун сўзларни эслаб қўйиш жараёни содир бўлади. Агар шундай бўлса, визуал хотиранинг аҳамиятини эътибордан четда қолдириб бўлмайди. Қишлоқ хўжалиги соҳаларининг номларини рус тилида ўзлаштиришда қуйидаги иш турини таклиф қилишингиз мумкин:

Подпишите подходящие слова под рисунком.

Слова для справок: хлопководство, каракулеводство, бахчеводство, скотоводство, пчеловодство, бахчеводство, рыбоводство, птицеводство, грибоводство, лесоводство, цветоводство...

Ушбу турдаги визуал луғатлар техник олий таълим муассасаларининг таҳсил олаётган талабаларига ўз мутахассисликлари бўйича эслаб қолиш қийин бўлган атамаларни осонгина эслаб қолишга ёрдам беради.

Матнлар тематикаси билан боғлиқ машқларни мақсадли танлаш лексик бирликларни юқори даражадаги такрорийлигини таъминлайди, бу уларни ғайриихтиёрий равишда ёдлашга ҳисса қўшади. Луғат устида ишлаш унинг оғзаки ва нутқ фаолиятида амалий қўлланилиши билан яқунланади. Нутқ машқларини бажариш лексик материал эркин ўзлаштириш ўз ичига олади.

Биз таклиф этаётган машқлар, табиийки, янада мукамалликни талаб қилади. Бизнинг мақсадимиз, уни амалда тадбиқ қилиш, бизнинг назаримизда, уни амалда ижобий тадбиқ этиш техник олий таълим муассасалари талабаларига рус тилида касбий нутқни ўрганиш учун кенг ва ишончли асос яратади.

Касбий йўналтирилган нутқнинг лексик қўникмаларини самарали шакллантириш машқларнинг мунтазамлик ва тизимлик хусусиятига боғлиқ, чунки тизимлилик муваффақиятнинг асосидир [2].

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TILSHUNOSLIKDAGI DOLZARB MASALALAR

CURRENT ISSUES IN LINGUISTICS

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN STUDYING FRENCH AND ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Abstract: This article discusses the difference between studying French and English grammar. It explains that every language has its own rules, pronunciation, and intonation. While learning any language fluently, it is significant to study grammar, practice speaking, listen to songs, watch movies, and communicate with others. The meticulous investigations have been carried out as a result of which, literature review is included in the article.

Keywords: English, Diversity, Intonation, Pronunciation, Rules of study.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается о разнице между изучением грамматики французского и английского языков. В нем объясняется, что в каждом языке есть свои правила, произношение и интонация. Чтобы хорошо выучить любой язык, важно изучать грамматику, практиковаться в разговорной речи, слушать песни, смотреть фильмы и общаться с другими людьми.

Ключевые слова: Английский язык, разнообразие, Интонация, произношение, Правила изучения.

Аннотасија: Ushbu maqola Ingliz va Fransuz tillarini o'rganishda grammatikaning har xilligini tahlil qiladi. Bunda, har bir tilning o'z grammatik, talaffuz va intonatsiya qoidalari, umuman olgandas o'ziga xosligini ta'kidlab o'tish lozim. Istalagan tilni mukammal o'rganish uchun, uning grammatikasini tahlil qilish, ushbu tilda nutqni o'stirish, va masalan, qo'shiq tinglash yoki ushbu tilda videolar ko'rish orqali muloqotni o'stirish lozim. Bu soha sinchkovlik bilan o'rganilib, maqolada adabiyotlar tahlili orqali mavzu keng yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tili, turfa xillik, ohang, talaffuz, qoidalar.

Introduction

In our vast world, where people of different nationalities live, there are languages through which they communicate and understand each other. Each language has its own unique grammar, pronunciation, intonation, and rules for studying words.

When conversing with a foreigner, you can immediately tell which country you are from. To master and learn any language, you must study the grammar, starting with the simplest exercises, learning the alphabet, learning to pronounce letters and the words that go with them, study parts of speech, learn to compose sentences and dialogues with them, and also practice every day, listen songs, watch movies, and have simple conversations with the words you have learned on different topics.

Main Part

The notion of “ grammar” has been the crucial part of English teaching up to recent years from ancient times. As Grammar-Translation method was one of the leading ways of teaching last century and many claimed this method to be inefficient in terms of improving communication in the target language. Along with European linguists Uzbek linguists have investigated benefits and drawbacks of studying and teaching of grammar while learning a language (Khalikova 2024; Nasriddinov 2023; Zakhidova 2024).

According to Comrie the study of grammar in second language acquisition (SLA) presents varying levels of complexity depending on the linguistic structures of the target language. French and English, although both Indo-European languages, differ significantly in grammatical structure, morphology, and syntactic organization. This review explores key research findings that highlight the challenges, instructional methods, and learner perceptions associated with studying the grammar of French and English.

For example, when studying the topic “Season”, you need to learn poems about this topic and practice with friends. When studying a chosen language, you need to know that each language has its own unique grammar and be able to pronounce and distinguish the use of certain words. For example, before an English noun, a function word isn't always present, but before a French noun, a function word is present in most cases. A function word in French as in English is never stressed. A common concept in learning the pronunciation of English and French words is the ability to correctly pronounce sounds and only then words. A French phrase is divided not into words but into groups of words. In English, however, words can be pronounced separately. French consonant sounds, like English ones, are never politalized before vowels. The main characteristic of French syntax is that it has a fixed word order in a sentence – subject-verb-object, and in English, the word order in a sentence is also fixed. However, in some cases, an adverbial phrase can appear at the beginning of a sentence. It should also be noted that articles are not always translated in both English and French. When listening to poems or songs in English and French, one can notice a significant difference in articulation. This clearly demonstrates how different these languages are. Yet, each is unique in its own way. When learning any world-class language, the most accessible and engaging methods should be used. The methods facilitate memorization of difficult grammatical structures and their application in composing dialogues and texts on a given topic. Visual aids should also be used concurrently. Then it's possible to learn several languages and even take a cruise to countries where those languages are spoken.

According to DeKeyser, R. M. English is generally classified as an analytic language, relying on word order and auxiliary constructions, whereas French is

considered more synthetic, with rich morphological inflections. According to Comrie (1981) and Greenberg (1966), typological classification affects how grammatical concepts are internalized by learners. French grammar involves complex verb conjugation systems, noun-adjective agreement, and gender distinctions, which are largely absent or reduced in English grammar (Hawkins & Towell, 2001). According to Ellis, R. Numerous studies have investigated how learners acquire grammatical forms in both languages. VanPatten (1996) proposed the Input Processing model, emphasizing that French learners require a different form-focus in instruction due to the difficulty of processing clitics and agreement markers. In contrast, Krashen's (1982) Input Hypothesis posits that English grammar can often be acquired through naturalistic exposure to comprehensible input, reducing the need for explicit grammar instruction.

According to Greenberg instructional approaches differ across English and French language teaching contexts. French grammar instruction often adopts form-focused instruction (FFI), involving drills and rule explanation (Spada & Lightbown, 1999), while Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) are more common in English language education. Ellis (2006) distinguishes between deductive and inductive grammar instruction, noting that deductive approaches are more prevalent in French teaching due to its grammatical intricacies.

According to Hawkins, R., & Towell, R. SLA research has documented distinct interlanguage patterns in learners of French and English. According to Lyster (1998), French learners often struggle with gender assignment, verb conjugations, and pronoun placement, whereas English learners encounter difficulties with article use, tense/aspect combinations, and word order (Swan & Smith, 2001). These error patterns suggest the need for differentiated instructional strategies.

It is also important to know that the phonetic aspect of French is more complex than that of English. Furthermore, a learner should know that minimal grammatical knowledge alone will not ensure the ability to speak. Special attention should be paid to the study of collocation and locally spoken language, consisting of questions, answers, remarks and short exclamations. Such everyday conversation situations gradually reinforce grammatical concepts in any language. Dialect pronunciation exercises help to pronounce French vowel sounds correctly, as they differ from English vowels in the intensity of their articulation. The articulation of French vowels involves the muscles of the lips, tongue, cheeks, and palate. English vowels are easier and more accessible for speakers to pronounce. Comparing these two languages makes it clear how important it is to find the right engaging way to learn difficult grammatical points and to memorize complex rules. The desire to practice pronunciation of sounds and

words, to construct sentences with new words, and to develop the ability to incorporate these words into everyday exercise is essential for learning any language.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while both French and English grammar serve the same fundamental purpose of structuring language for clear communication, they differ significantly in rules, complexity, and structure. French grammar often involves more rigid gender rules, verb conjugations, and agreement patterns, making it more intricate in some respects. English grammar, on the other hand, tends to be more flexible but presents its own challenges, especially with irregular verbs and exceptions. Understanding these differences is essential for language learners, as it helps them adapt their learning strategies to each language's unique characteristics and avoid confusion. Ultimately, recognizing and appreciating the distinct grammatical systems of French and English can lead to a deeper mastery of both languages.

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Hind-Yevropa tillari oilasi oxud nemis tili

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Hind-Yevropa tillari oilasining tarkibi va rivojlanish tarixi, shuningdek, nemis tilining bu oiladagi o'rni, shaklan xususiyatlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Maqolada nemis tilining tarixi, kelib chiqishi va uning hozirgi zamon tillari bilan bog'liqligi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, nemis tilining boshqa Hind-Yevropa tillaridan farqlanishi, uning grammatikasi va leksikasining o'ziga xos jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola tilshunoslik, tarix va madaniyat o'rganuvchilariga nemis tilining rivojlanish jarayonini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Hind-Yevropa tillari oilasi, nemis tili grammatikasi, tilshinoslik, omonim, sinonim, shakldoshlar, leksik xususiyatlar, g'arbiy german tili.

Аннотация

В этой статье представлена информация о составе и истории развития индоевропейских языков, а также о месте немецкого языка в этой семье и его морфологических особенностях. в статье анализируется история немецкого языка его происхождение и связь современными языками. кроме того рассматриваются различия немецкого языка, его происхождение и связь с современными языками кроме того рассматриваются различия немецкого языка от других индоевропейских языков, его грамматические и лексические особенности. статья помогает изучающим язык лучше понять процесс развития немецкого языка с точки зрения лингвистики, истории и культуры.

Ключевые слова: Индоевропейская языковая семья, грамматика немецкого языка, лингвистика, омонимы, синонимы, формы слов, лексические особенности, западногерманская группа.

Abstract

This article provides information about the structure and historical development of the indoeuropean language family, as well as the place of the german language in this family and its morphological characteristics. the article analyzes the history of the german language, its origin, and its connection with modern languages. additionally, it examines how the german language, its origin, and its connection with modern languages. additionally, it examines how the german language, differs from other indoeuropean languages, as well as its unique grammatical and lexical features. This article helps linguists, historians and cultural researchers understand the process of the german languages development.

Keywords: Indo-European language family, German language grammar, linguistics, homonyms, synonyms, word forms, lexical features, West Germanic language group.

Dunyoda so'z jihatdan eng boy tillar arab va ingliz tillari hisoblanadi. Ingliz tilida ikki yarim milliondan ortiq, arab tilida uch yarim milliondan ortiq lug'at boyligi mavjud [2]. Tilshunoslik fanidan ma'lumki, qaysi tilda sinonimlar, ya'ni ma'nodosh so'zlar ko'p bo'lsa, o'sha til eng boy til; shuningdek, qaysi tilda shakldoshlar – omonim so'zlar ko'p bo'lsa, o'sha til eng kambag'al til deb yuritiladi. Masalan, shimoliy qutbda yashaydigan eskimos qabilasiga mansub millat tilida “qor” so'zining 20 xil sinonimi mavjud. Arab tilida esa “cho'l” so'zining 100 dan ortiq varianti bor. Yer kurrasi bo'ylab eng ko'p tarqalgan tillardan biri ispan tilidir. Ispan tilining bu darajadagi keng tarqalishiga sabab, avvalo, mashhur dengiz sayyohlari, qaroqchilar, Ispaniya mustamlakachilari sabab bo'lgan. Hatto AQSHning 50 ta shtatidan 23 tasida davlat tili sifatida ispan tilidan foydalaniladi. Tillar bir-biriga yaqinligiga ko'ra til oilalarga bo'linadi. Yer yuzasida tillarning qardoshligiga ko'ra quyidagi til oilalari mavjud [2].

Hind-Yevropa tillari oilasi

- Oltoy tillar oilasi.
- Fin-ugor tillar oilasi.
- Som-xom tillari oilasi.
- Kavkaz tillari oilasi.
- Xitoy-tibet tillari oilasi.

Bular orasida eng keng tarqalgani “Hind-Yevropa tillari oilasi” hisoblanadi. Bu oilaga *slavyan* guruhi (belarus, rus, ukrain, chex, slovak, polyak, makedon, serb, xorvat, sloven), *german* guruhi (ingliz, nemis, sved, norveg, dat, island, golland tillari), *roman* guruhi (fransuz, ispan, portugal, italyan, rumin, moldavan tillari), *boltiq* guruhi (litva, latish, latgal tillari), *eron* guruhi (fors, afg'on, osetin, kurd, tojik, va boshqa tillar), *hind* guruhi (hind, urdu, bengal, panjob, gujarat kabi tillar) kiradi. Yuqorida ko'rsatilgani kabi bu til oilasi asosan Yevropa, Hindiston, Eron kabi hududlarda keng tarqalgan.

“Hind-yevropa tillari oilasi” atamasi 1813-yili mashhur ingliz olimi Tomas Yang tomonidan kiritilgan. Hind-yevropa tillari oilasi tilshunoslar tomonidan qiyosiy tarixiy metod yordamida isbotlangan katta o'xshashlik tamoyillari asosida ajratilgan. U 200 ga yaqin tirik va o'lik aloqa vositalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu tillar oilasi soni 2,5 milliarddan ortiq so'zlovchilar tomonidan ifodalanadi. Shu bilan birga, ularning nutqi ma'lum bir davlat chegarasida to'planib qolmay, butun yer yuzi bo'ylab tarqaladi. Tilshunoslar “Hind-yevropa tillari oilasini” qayerdan kelib chiqqanligiga qiziqmoqda. Unga ko'ra bu til oilasi haqidagi qarashlarda bir qancha gipotezalar bor. Ular “Anadolu gipotezasi”, “Kurgan gipotezasi”, “Bolqon gipotezasi”dir [5]. Hind-yevropa tillari oilasi tarkibida ko'plab til oilalari guruhi bor. Ammo bu til oilasidagi german guruhi tarkibiga kiradigan nemis tili alohida ahamiyatga ega. Chunki nemis tili (Deutsch) hozirgi kunda nafaqat iqtisodiy aloqalarda, balki Yevropa ittifoqining asosiy tili

sifatida foydalanilmoqda. Xo'sh, nima sababdan nemis tili bu darajada keng tarqaldi? Biz bu savolga javob berish uchun uning tarixiga nazar tashlashimiz kerak [3].

Qadimgi german tili (mil. avv. 1000- yillar va mil. IX asr boshlarida) nemis tilining tarixiy ildizi qadimgi german tiliga borib taqaladi. Bu tildan Germaniya, Skandinaviya va Yevropada yashagan qadimgi german xalqlari foydalangan. Qadimgi german tilining o'zi dialektlarga bo'lingan bo'lib, ularning barchasi German tillari oilasining asosini tashkil etgan. Bu davrda nemis tili hali to'liq shakllanmagan, ammo german tilining ba'zi so'zlari va grammatikasi hozirgi nemis tiliga ta'sir ko'rsatgan.

Ilk o'rta asrlar (V-X asrlar). V asrda Rim imperiyasining qulashidan keyin german xalqlari Yevropaning turli mintaqalariga tarqaldi. Bu davrda german tilining erkin shakllari mavjud bo'lib, ularning orasida g'arbiy german tili (Germaniya va uning atrofidagi hududlarda) o'z taraqqiyotini boshladi. Germaniya hududida, ayniqsa, fransuzlar, inglizlar, gollandlar bilan tillarning aloqalari ko'p bo'ldi. Bu davrda nemis tilining Alamanni (janubiy nemis dialekti), Bavariya va Saksoniya kabi o'ziga xos dialektlari mavjud edi. Bu dialektlar asta-sekin birlashib, o'zgarib bordi va keyinchalik nemis tilining asosini tashkil etdi.

O'rta asrlar (XI-XV asrlar). XI asrda nemis tili o'zining shakllanish jarayonini davom ettirdi. O'rta nemis tili (Mittelhochdeutsch) davrida, til ko'proq yozma shaklda rivojlanib, turli adabiy asarlar yaratilgan. Shu davrda Dante Alighieri va Geoffery Chaucer kabi yozuvchilarga o'xshab, nemis tilida ham ko'plab adabiy asarlar vujudga keldi. "Nibelungenlied" ("Nibelunlar qo'shig'I") nomli epopeya, o'rta nemis tilining eng mashhur asari hisoblanadi. XV asrning oxiriga kelib, Johann Gutenbergning bosma matbaa (kitob bosish dastgohi) ixtirosi nemis tilining kengroq tarqalishiga yordam berdi, bu esa nemis adabiyotining va ilmiy fikrlarning o'sishiga olib keldi.

Yangi nemis tili (XVI-XVIII asrlar) XVI asrda, Martin Lyuterning "Bibliya"ni nemis tiliga tarjima qilishi nemis tilining rivojlanishida katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Lyuterning tarjimasini nemis tilining o'rta asr shaklidan rivojlanishiga yordam berdi va u nemis tilining standartlashishiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi. XVII-XVIII asrlarda nemis tili Yangi nemis tili (Neuhochdeutsch) deb nomlanuvchi shakliga o'tib, grammatik jihatdan ko'proq tizimlashdi va so'z boyligi kengaydi. Bu davrda tilning yasalishi ancha oddiylashdi va kengroq qo'llanila boshladi.

XIX-XX asrlarda nemis tilining yanada rivojlanishi. XIX asrda Germaniya birlashgach, nemis tili yagona davlat tili sifatida joriy etildi. Bu davrda nemis tili ilmfan, adabiyot va madaniyatda katta ahamiyatga ega bo'ldi. G'arbiy Yevropada, shuningdek, ilmiy va texnikaviy til sifatida o'z o'rnini topdi.

XX asrda nemis tili dunyoda keng tarqaldi, ayniqsa, iqtisodiy, ilmiy va madaniy jihatdan Germaniya va Avstriyaning kuchli ta'siri tufayli. Hozirgi kunda nemis tili Yevropa ittifoqining rasmiy tillaridan biri va jahondagi eng ko'p o'rganiladigan tillardan biridir. Shuningdek, hozirgi kunda nemis tilini hind-yevropa tillari oilasining

german guruhi tarkibiga kiruvchi ingliz, niderland, shved, dan, island, tillari bilan tahlil qilib chiqish lozimdir. Chunki nemis tilini bu tillar o'rtasida grammatik va leksik jihatdan ko'plab o'xshashliklari bor.

Ingliz tili bilan bog'liqligi

- *Ingliz va nemis tillari german tillari oilasining g'arbiy guruhiga mansub*
- *Ikkala til ham ko'plab umumiy ildiz so'zlariga ega:
Haus-house, Wasser-water, Mutter-mother.*
- *Grammatik jihatdan ingliz tili soddalshgan bo'lsa-da, tarixiy ildizlari bir xildir*

Slavyan tillari bilan aloqadorlik

- *Nemis tili tarixiy rivojlanishida slavyan tillari, ayniqsa, polyak va chex tillari bilan muloqatda bo'lgandir.*
- *Ayniqsa, chegaradosh hududlarda leksik ta'sir mavjud: ayrim o'zlashgan so'zlar va talaffuz unsurlari bor.*

Roman tillari (fransuz, italyan, ispan, tillari) bilan munosabat

- *O'rta asrlardan boshlab fransuz tilidan nemis tiliga ko'plab so'zlar o'zlashgan bo'lib, ayniqsa, diplomatiya, san'at va madaniyat sohalarida.*
- *Hozirgi globalizatsiya davrida ingliz tili orqali yana ko'plab so'zlar boshqa tillarga singmoqda, shu jumladan nemis tiliga ham.*

Fonetik va grammatik o'xshashliklar

- *Hozirgi zamon tillari, ayniqsa, Yevropa tillari, fonetik tizimlarda ayrim umumiyliklarga ega. Masalan, artikl ishlatilishi (ingliz, nemis, fransuz).*
- *Fe'l zamonlari va so'z tartibi jihatdan ham umumiy tendensiyalar mavjuddir (masalan, qo'shimchalar o'rniga yordamchi fe'llardan foydalanish)*

Bundan tashqari nemis tili hind-yevropa tillaridan farqlanishi, grammatikasi leksikasining o'ziga xos jihatlarini ko'rib chiqish lozimdir.

1. Nemis tilining boshqa hind-yevropa tillaridan farqlanishi:

- *Fonetika jihatdan: Nemis tilida "ch" (ich, Buch) kabi tovushlar mavjud bo'lib, bu ko'pchilik hind-yevropa tillarida uchramaydi.*
- *So'z tartibi: Nemis tilida fe'l odatda gapning ikkinchi o'rnida yoki ergashgan gaplar oxirida keladi. Bu jihat ingliz yoki italyan tilidan sezilarli darajada farq qiladi.*
- *Majmua so'zlari (kompozitlar): nemis tilida uzun va murakkab so'zlar yasash uchun keng tarqalgan (masalan, Donaudampfschiffahrtsgesellschaftskapitan)*
- *Ot jinslari: nemis tilida otlar erkak (der), ayol (die), va o'rta (das) jinslarga bo'linadi. Bu xususiyatlar ba'zi boshqa tillarda (masalan, ingliz tilida) yo'qolgan.*

4. Grammatik o'ziga xosliklar:

- *Kelishiklar (Kasuslar): nemis tilida otlar va olmoshlar to'rt kelishikda o'zgaradi: Nominativ, Genitiv, Dativ, Akkusativ.*

- *Fe'l zamonlari: fe'l zamonlari (hozirgi, o'tgan, kelasi va Perfekt zamonlar) murakkab tuzilmalarda ifodalanadi.*

- *Fe'lning ajraluvchi qo'shimchalari: ba'zi fe'llarda 682refix gap oxiriga o'tadi. (masalan: aufstehn – Ich stehe um 7 Uhr auf)*

- *Artikllar tizimi: belgili va belgisiz artikllar jins, son va kelishiklarga qarab o'zgaradi.*

5. Leksik xususiyatlari:

- *Nemischa so'zlar ko'pincha germantik ildizga ega, ya'ni lotincha yoki yunoncha ildizlardan ko'proq foydalaniladi (ingliz tiliga qaraganda ko'proq).*

- *Yangi so'z yasash: Nemis tili yangi atamalarni o'z ildizlaridan foydalanilgan holda yaratishga moyil, boshqa tillar esa ko'pincha lotin yoki inglizcha atamalarni to'g'ridan to'g'ri oladi.*

- *Sinonimlar va murakkab so'zlar ko'pligi: til boy leksikaga ega bo'lib, har bir tushunchani ifodalash uchun bir nechta turli so'zlar ishlatiladi.*

Hozirgi davrda nemis tili ommaviy axborot vositalarida va jahon siyosatida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Yevropa ittifoqining rasmiy tili bo'lmish nemis tiliga qiziqish dunyo yoshlarining orasida ortmoqda. Nemis tili bugungi kunda nafaqat Hind-yevropa tillari oilasida, balki butun dunyoda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Xulosa

Hind-yevropa tillari oilasi – bugungi kunda insoniyat tarixida eng keng tarqalgan va eng ko'p o'rganilgan til oilalaridan biridir. Bu til oilasiga kiruvchi tillar geografik, tarixiy va madaniy jihatdan keng hududlarni qamrab olib, butun insoniyat tarqqiyotiga beqiyos hissa qo'shib kelmoqdadir. Ayniqsa, bu oiladagi nemis tilining o'rni va o'ziga xosliklari beqiyosdir. Nemis tili o'zining tarixiy ildizlari bilan qadimgi german tillariga borib taqaladi. Tarixiy bosqichlar davomida bu til turli omillar, ya'ni urushlar, migratsiyalar, madaniy va siyosiy aloqalar, diniy harakatlar ta'sirida shakllanib, hozirgi mukammal va rivojlangan holatga yetdi. Martin Lyuter tomonidan "Bibliya"ning tarjimasini nemis tilining adabiy va grammatik jihatdan mustahkamlanishiga zamin yaratdi. XIX asrdan boshlab esa Germaniyaning siyosiy va iqtisodiy kuchayishi bilan bu til ilm-fan, sanoat va madaniyatda yetakchi mavqega ega bo'ldi. Nemis tilining boshqa tillar bilan bo'lgan aloqalari ham mazkur tilning shakllanishida muhim rol o'ynadi. ingliz, slavyan va roman tillari bilan bo'lgan o'zaro ta'sirlari natijasida nemis tili yanada boyidi, global miqyosda foydalanuvchilar soni ortdi. Bugungi globallashuv davrida nemis tili nafaqat Yevropa ittifoqining rasmiy tillaridan biri, balki jahon miqyosida o'rganilayotgan eng muhim tillardan biri bo'lib bormoqdadir. U iqtisodiyot, madaniyat, diplomatiya, san'at va madaniyat sohalarida

keng qo'llanilib, yosh avlod uchun zamonaviy bilim olish uchun va xalqaro maydonda faoliyat yuritish imkonini bermoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, nemis tili nafaqat Hind-yevropa tillari oilasidagi muhim til, balki dunyo sivilizatsiyasi taraqqiyotida o'ziga xos mavqega ega bo'lgan boy va sarmazmun til hisoblanadi. Uning o'rganilishi orqali nafaqat lingvistik bilimlar, balki tarix, madaniyat va xalqaro aloqalar haqida ham chuqur tasavvurga ega bo'lish mumkindir.

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THE LINGUOCULTURAL APPROACH TO TEACHING WORK WITH MEDIA TEXTS

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Abstract. In education, the linguocultural approach of teaching focuses on language and culture integration as parts of communication. Within media literacy, this approach serves as an ideal tool for fostering students' analytical abilities, inter/cross-cultural sensitivity, and language skills. In this article, I discuss the role and importance of the mediacultural approach to the work with media texts, describe important didactic techniques for teaching, and analyze the advantages of this research in contemporary education.

Key words: media texts, analyze, and create media texts, linguocultural approach, cultural meanings, cultural knowledge, globalized media predominate, etc.

Аннотация. Лингвокультурный подход в образовании подчеркивает интеграцию языка и культуры как неразрывных компонентов коммуникации. В контексте медиаграмотности этот подход предлагает мощную основу для развития у студентов критического мышления, межкультурной компетенции и коммуникативных навыков. В

данной статье рассматривается значение лингвокультурного подхода в обучении работе с медиатекстами, описываются эффективные педагогические стратегии и подчеркиваются преимущества этой методики в современных образовательных условиях.

Ключевые слова: медиатексты, анализ и создание медиатекстов, лингвокультурологический подход, культурные смыслы, культурное знание, глобализация медиа и др.

Annotatsiya. Ta'limdagi lingvomadaniy yondashuv til va madaniyatning aloqaning ajralmas tarkibiy qismi sifatida integratsiyalashuviga urg'u beradi. Media savodxonligi kontekstida bu yondashuv talabalarning tanqidiy fikrlash, madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun kuchli asosni taklif etadi. Ushbu maqolada media-matnlarni o'qitishda lingvomadaniy yondashuvning ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi, samarali pedagogik strategiyalar tavsiflanadi va zamonaviy ta'lim sharoitida ushbu uslubning afzalliklari ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mediamatnlar, mediatekstlarni tahlil qilish va yaratish, lingvamadaniy yondashuv, madaniy ma'nolar, madaniy bilimlar, media globallashuvi va boshqalar.

In a time where digital communication and global media prevail, the skill to analyze media texts critically is increasingly vital. Media texts—spanning news reports, advertisements, social media updates, and visual content—serve not only as linguistic creations but also as cultural products that both mirror and influence societal norms, values, and ideologies. The linguocultural perspective perceives language and culture as closely connected, providing an effective method for instructing students on how to interpret, analyze, and create media texts with a sophisticated grasp of both linguistic structure and cultural background. The integration of language and culture as integral parts of communication is emphasized by the linguocultural approach in education. This method provides a strong framework for fostering students' critical thinking, intercultural competency, and communication abilities within the framework of media literacy. This article describes successful pedagogical techniques, examines the value of the linguocultural approach in teaching work with media texts, and emphasizes the advantages of this methodology in contemporary educational environments.

It is more crucial than ever to be able to critically interact with media texts at a time when digital communication and globalized media predominate. In addition to being linguistic artifacts, media texts—from news stories and ads to social media posts and audiovisual content—are cultural products that represent and influence societal norms, values, and ideologies. Students can learn how to perceive, evaluate, and create media texts with a nuanced knowledge of both linguistic form and cultural context by using the linguocultural approach, which sees language and culture as intricately entwined.

The Linguocultural Approach: A Definition. The basis of the linguocultural approach is the notion that language is a vehicle for culture and that comprehending the cultural codes included in linguistic expressions is necessary for efficient

communication. This method focuses on the sociocultural consequences that language use transmits rather than just grammar and vocabulary.

In language education, particularly in foreign or second language instruction, the linguocultural approach seeks to:

Enhance learners' intercultural awareness

Promote cultural empathy

Develop contextually appropriate language use

When applied to media texts, this approach encourages students to deconstruct texts not only for their linguistic features but also for the cultural narratives they encode.

Media Texts as Linguocultural Artifacts. Media texts are ideal tools for implementing the linguocultural approach because they are:

Culturally situated: *Reflecting specific social, historical, and political contexts.*

Multimodal: *Combining text, image, and sound, which requires multilayered interpretation.*

Ideologically loaded: *Shaping and reflecting public opinion and values.*

For example, a commercial in the United States might reflect individualism and consumerism, whereas a similar ad in Japan may emphasize community and harmony. Teaching students to recognize and interpret these cultural cues enhances their media literacy and intercultural competence.

Teaching Strategies

1. Comparative Analysis of Media Texts. Encourage students to compare media texts from different cultural backgrounds on similar topics (e.g., news coverage of the same event in different countries). This strategy helps learners identify cultural biases and differing perspectives.

2. Discourse and Semiotic Analysis. Guide students in analyzing both the language and symbolic elements of media texts. Ask them to consider questions like: What cultural assumptions are embedded in the language? How do colors, images, and sounds contribute to meaning?

3. Media Text Production. Have students create their own media content (e.g., podcasts, blog posts, short videos) that reflects specific cultural values or is intended for a culturally distinct audience. This fosters active engagement with both language and cultural norms.

4. Critical Reflection and Discussion. Use classroom discussions to reflect on the influence of culture on perception. Encourage students to articulate how their own cultural background affects their interpretation of media.

Benefits of the Linguocultural Approach.

Enhances Critical Thinking: Students learn to question and evaluate the messages and assumptions in media texts.

Builds Intercultural Competence: Learners develop sensitivity to cultural differences and the ability to communicate across cultures.

Improves Language Proficiency: Students engage with authentic language use in real-world contexts.

Promotes Empathy and Global Awareness: Understanding other cultures through media fosters more tolerant and informed global citizens.

Challenges and Considerations. Despite its many benefits, implementing the linguocultural approach can be challenging. Teachers must be equipped with cultural knowledge, and curricula must allow for flexibility and depth. Moreover, students may initially struggle with analyzing implicit cultural meanings or navigating unfamiliar value systems. To address these challenges, professional development for educators and access to diverse media sources are essential.

The linguocultural approach to teaching work with media texts offers a rich, multidimensional framework that prepares students for the complexities of global communication. By integrating language learning with cultural analysis, educators can cultivate media-literate learners who are not only proficient in language but also adept at navigating the cultural nuances of our interconnected world.

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Lexical Analysis of Parts of Speech in Uzbek and English

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi so'z turkumlarining leksik xususiyatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. So'z turkumlari til tizimidagi muhim bo'g'in sifatida grammatik va semantik jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. So'z turkumlari leksik birliklar asosida ajratilib, har ikki til misolida turli omillar: morfologik qurilish, semantik xususiyatlar, va sintaktik funksiyalari asosida tavsiflanadi. Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarining turlilik jihatlari, xususan, yasalma va tayyor birliklar orqali tuzilgan so'z turkumlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z turkumlari, leksik tahlil, o'zbek tili, ingliz tili, grammatik tizim, morfologiya.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проводится сравнительно-лексический анализ частей речи узбекского и английского языка. Рассмотрены особенности грамматической классификации, функционально-синтаксические и морфологические свойства частей речи в каждом языке. Статья основана на принципах лексико-семантического анализа.

Ключевые слова: части речи, лексико-семантический анализ, узбекский язык, английский язык, грамматика, морфология.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative lexical analysis of parts of speech in Uzbek and English. It explores the grammatical and semantic characteristics of word classes in both languages. The study addresses morphological construction, syntactic functions, and the classification of lexical units, offering detailed comparison supported by examples. By applying the principles of lexico-semantic analysis and drawing on the cognitive-semantic approach, the article emphasizes both similarities and unique features of the systems.

Keywords: parts of speech, lexical analysis, Uzbek language, English language, grammar, morphology.

1. Introduction

Parts of speech are essential building blocks in any language's structure. They determine how words function in sentences and how meanings are constructed and conveyed. In both Uzbek and English, the classification of words into grammatical categories reflects deep linguistic, cultural, and historical backgrounds. This study aims to explore how lexical elements in each part of speech (e.g., nouns, verbs, adjectives) compare across Uzbek and English languages.

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of this study is rooted in both traditional and modern linguistic frameworks. Classical grammar, as described in structural linguistics, often organizes words into fixed categories based on morphological features and syntactic

roles (Crystal, 2008). However, contemporary linguistics has expanded this view through cognitive and functional perspectives, arguing that parts of speech are not only structural elements but also cognitive tools reflecting speakers' conceptualization of the world (Evans & Green, 2006).

Lexical semantics, a branch of linguistic semantics, plays a central role in understanding the meaning and classification of words. According to Murphy (2010), lexical meaning involves a combination of definitional, associative, and contextual elements. These aspects influence how words are categorized and used in real discourse.

In agglutinative languages like Uzbek, parts of speech are often identified through affixation, where lexical and grammatical meanings are conveyed via suffixes rather than function words. In contrast, English uses auxiliary verbs, word order, and syntactic constructions to serve similar functions (Yule, 2017).

Furthermore, sociolinguistic studies (e.g., Turgunov, 2023) demonstrate how cultural context and emotional values shape lexical fields and parts of speech. For instance, interjections and modal particles in Uzbek can reflect speaker attitude and social hierarchy, features not as strongly marked in English grammar.

Functional approaches emphasize the use of parts of speech in communicative contexts. For example, Hopper and Thompson (1984) propose that syntactic categories emerge from discourse patterns rather than pre-established grammatical rules. This usage-based perspective supports a dynamic view of word classes and underscores the role of frequency, salience, and cognitive economy in shaping grammar.

These frameworks enable a holistic and comparative analysis of parts of speech in Uzbek and English, revealing how linguistic form, function, and meaning are interconnected in different typological systems.

3. Nouns and numbers Nouns are central to both English and Uzbek grammatical systems. They denote objects, people, places, concepts, and phenomena. English nouns can be countable or uncountable, singular or plural, and are marked for possession using apostrophe-s ('s) (Yule, 2017). In contrast, Uzbek nouns often undergo extensive morphological changes to reflect case, number, and possession.

For instance:

- English: *student – students – student's book*
- Uzbek: *talaba – talabalar – talabaning kitobi*

Semantically, numerals carry both quantificational and ordering functions in both languages, but their syntactic mobility and morphological integration differ. English maintains a clear syntactic separation of numerals and other parts of speech, while Uzbek frequently blends numerals into nominal and adjectival constructions (Turgunov, 2023).

An additional cultural-pragmatic distinction is the usage of numerals in evaluative or emotional contexts. For instance, in Uzbek, the numeral *bir* (one) may be used to express negative emphasis:

Bitta ham inson emas ekan u inson! (“Not even a single person can be called human!”)

This type of negative intensification via numeral is rarely found in English, where the equivalent construction would more likely use quantifiers or negation (*No one could call him human!*), but not the numeral *one* with the same emphatic pragmatics.

4. Verbs

Verbs express actions, states, or processes. English verbs are conjugated based on tense, aspect, mood, and voice. The tense system is well-developed, with distinctions among simple, continuous, perfect, and perfect continuous aspects (Murphy, 2010).

Uzbek verbs are also inflected for tense, mood, and person, but employ a more agglutinative structure. The verb root takes multiple suffixes to express grammatical meanings. Additionally, auxiliary verbs such as *edi*, *ekan*, *bo'ladi* expand the temporal and modal system.

Example:

- English: *He had been working.*
- Uzbek: *U ishlayotgan edi.*

5. Adjectives and Adverbs

English adjectives are typically placed before nouns (*a beautiful garden*) and do not inflect for gender or number. In Uzbek, adjectives precede nouns but may agree semantically without morphological changes.

Adverbs in English often end in *-ly* (*quick – quickly*), while in Uzbek they are often formed from adjectives by affixation or syntactic transformation (*tez – tezda*). Both languages use adverbs to modify verbs, adjectives, or entire sentences.

6. Pronouns and Determiners

Pronouns replace nouns and indicate grammatical person, number, gender, and case. English uses subject, object, possessive, reflexive, and relative pronouns. Uzbek has equivalents but the distinctions are often inferred through suffixes rather than word changes.

Example:

- English: *I gave him my book.*
- Uzbek: *Men unga kitobimni berdim.*

Determiners in English include articles (*a, an, the*), demonstratives, possessives, and quantifiers. Uzbek does not have articles but uses demonstratives (*bu, u*) and quantifiers similarly.

7. Conjunctions, Prepositions, and Particles

English uses prepositions (*in, on, at*) to indicate spatial, temporal, or logical relations. Uzbek uses postpositions or affixes to indicate such relations (*uyda, bog'da*).

Conjunctions such as *and, but, or* exist in both languages (*va, lekin, yoki*). Particles in Uzbek (e.g., *ku, -da, ham*) add emphasis, contrast, or clarification, and have no direct English equivalents.

8. Interjections

Interjections express emotion and are often standalone. English examples include *wow, oh, ouch*, while Uzbek equivalents include *voy, hay, yo'q!* These are culturally embedded and context-dependent, often indicating surprise, pain, or disbelief (Turgunov, 2023).

9. Morphological and Semantic Implications

Uzbek's agglutinative structure makes morphology central to word classification, while English leans more on syntax and word order. Semantic roles are often expressed through word position in English, but through suffixation in Uzbek.

10. Conclusion

The comparison of lexical categories in Uzbek and English reveals both structural and functional distinctions. Uzbek emphasizes agglutination and inflectional morphology, whereas English relies on auxiliary constructions and word order. Understanding these differences is crucial for linguistic analysis, translation, and second language acquisition.

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G'AYRIODATIY BIRIKMALARNING LINGVOPOETIK AKTUALLASHUVI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada g'ayriodatiy birikmalar va rang bildiruvchi so'zlarning estetik va poetik maqsadlarda ishlatilishi o'rganiladi. Ijodkorlarning g'ayriodatiy birikmalarda rang so'zlaridan qanday qilib mavhum, noaniq va metaforik mazmunlarni yaratishda foydalanishlari tushuntirilgan. Muallif, rang bildiruvchi so'zlarning aniq mazmunini o'zgarishini va ularning semantik qirralari orqali qanday yangi poetik tasvirlar va obrazlar hosil qilinishini misollar bilan namoyish etadi. Misol tariqasida, "yashil barg" va "yashil shabboda" birikmalari yordamida rang so'zlarining estetik maqsadlarda qanday yangi semantik qatlamlarni ochib berishi ko'rsatilgan. Bu jarayon g'ayriodatiy birikmalarni yaratishda metaforik epitetlar va tasviriy ifodalarni shakllantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: G'ayriodatiy birikmalar, rang bildiruvchi so'zlar, metafora, poetik obraz, semantika, estetik maqsad, yashil, shabboda, epitet, tasviriy ifoda.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается использование необычных сочетаний и цветовых обозначений в эстетических и поэтических целях. В нем объясняется, как создатели используют цветовые обозначения в необычных сочетаниях для создания абстрактных, неоднозначных и метафорических значений. Автор на примерах показывает, как меняется точное значение цветовых обозначений и как через их семантические аспекты создаются новые поэтические образы и образы. В качестве примера используются сочетания «зеленый лист» и «зеленый шаббат», чтобы показать, как цветовые слова раскрывают новые семантические слои в эстетических целях. Этот процесс формирует метафорические эпитеты и образные выражения, создавая необычные сочетания.

Ключевые слова: Необычные сочетания, цветовые слова, метафора, поэтический образ, семантика, эстетическое назначение, зеленый ветер, эпитет, образное выражение.

Abstract: This article studies the use of non-standard combinations and color words for aesthetic and poetic purposes. It explains how creators use color words in non-standard combinations to create abstract, ambiguous and metaphorical meanings. The author shows with examples how the specific meaning of color words changes and how new poetic images and images are created through their semantic aspects. As an example, the combinations "green leaf" and "green shabboda" show how new semantic layers of color words can be revealed for aesthetic purposes. This process forms metaphorical epithets and figurative expressions in the creation of non-standard combinations.

Keywords: Unusual combinations, color words, metaphor, poetic image, semantics, aesthetic purpose, green breeze, epithet, figurative expression.

G'ayriodatiy birikmalar orasida ularning shunday turlariga ham duch kelamizki, ijodkorlar g'ayriodatiy birikmalardagi so'zlardan birini muayyan estetik maqsad bilan rang bildiruvchi so'zlar orasidan ham tanlashi kuzatiladi. Bunda rang bildiruvchi so'zlardagi aniq mazmun mavhumlik tomon siljiydi. Shuningdek, bu mazmun tamoman muallaq, ajralgan holatda ro'y bermaydi, balki so'zdagi aniq mazmun o'rnida qo'llanish imkoniyatini beruvchi qirralari, uning rang-barang semalari

asosida yuzaga keladi. Masalan, *yashil barg* birikmasidagi yashil so'zi aniq bir mazmunni o'ta yorqin ifodalash maqsadida qo'llangan bo'lsa, *barg* so'zi o'rnida shabboda so'zi ishlatilganda, bu aniq mazmun o'zga qiyofa kasb eta boshlaydi. *Yashil shabboda* g'ayriodatiy birikmasidagi yashil so'zining konkretligi va moddiyligi rad etilishi hisobiga yashil so'zidagi mazmunning umumlashishi, ya'ni nomoddiylik tufayli bu so'z metaforik epitetga aylanadi. Shuningdek, "...shoir mazkur birikmani qo'llashga juda mohirona yondashgan, ya'ni shabboda yam-yashil maysazorda kezib yuribdi, u shu qadar nozikki, hatto "panjaradan oshib chiqib ketadi", ayni paytda hamma yoq "etni jimirlatar" darajada sof, beg'ubor, shuning uchun bunday shabboda faqat yashil bo'lishi mumkin xolos. Matnda yashil shabboda birikmasi juda chiroyli va ta'sirli yaxlit emotsional obrazning poetik ifodasiga aylangan.

Yer yosh, soflik jimirlatar etni,

Zoriqqan g'unchalar ochildi bog'da.

Panjaradan oshib chiqib ketdi

Maysazorda yurgan yashil shabboda. (A.M., «Tug'ilish»)"⁷⁸

She'rdagi *yashil* lug'aviy birligining ma'nosida ana shunday imkoniyat mavjud, ya'ni u tiniqlik, soflik, navqironlik, ko'rkamlilik kabi turli semalarni namoyish qilish imkoniyatiga ega. Yashil so'zining lug'aviy mundarijasidagi mana shu semik ifodalar hisobiga shabboda so'zi bilan semantik valentlik imkoniyatiga ega va muallif bu imkoniyatdan birinchilardan bo'lib foydalangan uchun ham ushbu birikma g'ayriodatiy birikma maqomidadir.

Ta'kidlanishicha, "...har qanday til belgisi lisoniy ma'noni kommunikativ jarayonda namoyon qilganligi kabi ideal, ruhiy-intellektual hodisa sifatidagi konsept ham kommunikativ jarayonda shakllanadi va tilning vositalari asosida mazkur jarayonda yuzaga chiqadi. Muayyan holatda so'z serqirra va ko'p o'lchamli konseptning ushbu kommunikativ jarayon uchun tegishli jihatlarini voqelantiradi. Demak, so'z ma'nosi zimmasida konseptning muloqot va axborot uchun zarur va daxldor bo'lgan jihatlarini namoyon qilish "mas'uliyat"i yotadi".⁷⁹

Yana bir namunada rang-tusni ifoda etuvchi *qora* so'zini "ma'lum qalinlikdagi yoki qat-qat yoyiq narsalar qavati"⁸⁰ni bildiruvchi *qatlam* so'zi bilan bog'lash orqali *qora qatlamlar* birikmasi tuziladi. Bu birikmada qora so'zining "ba'zi so'zlar bilan qo'llanib, ular anglatadigan narsaga xos belgi-holatning kuchli darajasini bildiruvchi"⁸¹ ma'nosi ishga solinadi. *Qora qatlamlar* birikmasi orqali o'tmishda bo'lib o'tgan, xotirada yomon iz qoldirgan xunuk voqealar, alamli, iztirobli hodisalarni

⁷⁸ Абдурахмонов Х., Махмудов Н. Сўз эстетикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 1981. – Б. 45.

⁷⁹ Suyarova N. "Belgi" denotativ semali metaforalarning tasnifi, kognitiv strukturasi va leksikografik talqini: Filol. fan. b-cha falsafa. d-ri. ... diss. avtoref. – Qarshi, 2021. – B. 16.

⁸⁰ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5-жилд. – Тошкент: "ЎЗМЭ", 2006. – Б. 336.

⁸¹ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5-жилд. – Тошкент: "ЎЗМЭ", 2006. – Б. 335.

ifodalash maqsad qilib olingan: *O'ylagan sari qora qatlamlar ochilib ketaverardi* (S.A., «Jimjitlik», 193-b.).

Ayrim hollarda esa *qora* so'zining “qorong'i, nursiz, ziyosiz”⁸² ma'nolari aktuallashib, *qora quchoq* birikmasi tuziladi va bu orqali badiiy obrazlilikni estetik tarzda ifoda etishning mukammal darajasiga erishiladi: *Bu kungi kech Otabek bilan Homidning hayot va mamot masalalarini o'zining qora quchog'iga olgan qorong'i bir tun edi* (A.Q., «O'tkan kunlar»).

G'ayriodatiy birikmalarda ba'zida yaxlit bir tushunchani poetik obrazda ifodalash imkoniyati mavjud ekanligi ham ko'zga tashlanadi: *Ilk tong nuri kiprigingga qo'nar, Ko'zdan yuvib ketar qora uyquni* (A.M., «Bolalik»). Parchadagi *qora uyqu* g'ayriodatiy birikmasi tun tushunchasining ifodasidir. Biroq *qora uyqu* birikmasi tun so'ziga qaraganda, mazmunan boyroq va poetik jarangdorroq hisoblanadi. Parchada keltirilgan *qora uyqu* nafaqat tunni, balki shu kecha bilan bog'langan boshqa narsalarning ifodasi hamdir. G'ayriodatiy birikmalardagi ekspressiv-emotsionallik ko'p hollarda individual xarakterda bo'lishi bois ushbu birikma ajoyib poetik obraz namunasiga aylangan. Mazkur bo'laklardagi so'zlar mazmunini har bir o'quvchi turlicha tushunishi mumkin. Ular o'zlarining idrok darajasiga ko'ra qora uyqu ifodasini individual holatda qabul qilishadi. Mualliflar “So'z estetikasi” nomli qo'llanmasida genial so'z san'atkori L.N.Tolstoyning o'lim dahshatini “qizil dahshat, oq kvadratli dahshat” sifatida ta'riflaganini ham qayd etadilar. Bundan tashqari, Rauf Parfidan quyidagi parchani keltiradilar:

“Og'ushimda zangori sezgi,

Kiprigimda suyuq hayajon,

Ko'zlarimda yumaloq sevgi,

Salomatman men ham, onajon. (R.P., «Yana qaytib keldim...»)

Mazkur she'riy parchadagi “zangori sezgi, suyuq hayajon va yumaloq sevgi birikmalari, avvalo, yangiligi, “tutilmaganligi” bilan tez diqqatni tortadi. Bizga ham undagi hissiy-emotsiyalar “yuqadi”⁸³.

Bizningcha ham, bu birikmalardan anglashilayotgan mazmun bizni lirik qahramonning hissiy holatidan ogoh etadi. Ayni damda ularning o'ta ta'sirchan emotsional obrazlar ekanligini sezamiz, lekin mana shu birikmalardagi *zangori, suyuq* va *yumaloq* so'zlari ifodalayotgan mazmunni turlicha tushunamiz, uni o'zimiz bilganicha idrok etamiz. Demakki, ularning ekspressiv-emotsionalligi holati ham turlichadir. Bundan ko'rinadiki, g'ayriodatiy birikmalardagi so'zlar ifodalashi mumkin bo'lgan mazmun turli darajada yuzaga chiqishi mumkin. Ba'zi hollarda esa yuqoridagi

⁸² Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5-жилд. – Тошкент: “ЎзМЭ”, 2006. – Б. 335.

⁸³ Абдурахмонов Х., Махмудов Н. Сўз эстетикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 1981. – Б. 45.

kabi abstraktsiya darajasi juda yuqori ham bo'lishi kuzatiladi. Bunday hollarda so'zlar o'zining konkret mazmunini deyarli yo'qotadi.

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O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA GUL NOMLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

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ANNOTATION

This article studies the comparative linguocultural, semantic and lexical analysis of flower names in Uzbek and English languages. Flower names are one of the important linguistic units that express the aesthetic views, national worldview and values of the people. The article analyzes their similarities and differences using the example of flower names in both languages, and highlights semantic inconsistencies, equivalence issues and cultural connotations in the translation process.

Keywords: flower names, comparative analysis, linguocultural, Uzbek language, English language, semantics, lexical difference.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье изучается сопоставительный лингвокультурологический, семантический и лексический анализ названий цветов в узбекском и английском языках. Названия цветов являются одной из важных языковых единиц, выражающих эстетические взгляды, национальное мировоззрение и ценности народа. В статье анализируются их сходства и различия на примере названий цветов в обоих языках, а также выделяются семантические несоответствия, проблемы эквивалентности и культурные коннотации в процессе перевода.

Ключевые слова: названия цветов, сопоставительный анализ, лингвокультурологический, узбекский язык, английский язык, семантика, лексическое различие.

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillarida gul nomlarining lingvokulturologik, semantik va leksik jihatdan qiyosiy tahlili o'rganiladi. Gul nomlari xalqning estetik qarashlari, milliy dunyoqarashi va qadriyatlarini ifodalovchi muhim til birliklaridan biri hisoblanadi. Maqolada har ikki tilda mavjud bo'lgan gul nomlari misolida ularning o'zaro o'xshash va farqli jihatlari tahlil qilinadi, tarjima jarayonidagi semantik nomuvofiqliklar, ekvivalentlik masalalari hamda madaniy konnotatsiyalar yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: gul nomlari, qiyosiy tahlil, lingvokulturologiya, o'zbek tili, ingliz tili, semantika, leksik tafovut.

KIRISH

Har qanday tilda gul nomlari nafaqat botanik atamalar, balki xalqning madaniyati, estetik qarashlari, tarixiy tajribasi va milliy tafakkurining yorqin ifodasidir. Ular ko'pincha ramziy ma'nolar, obrazli ifodalar, xalq og'zaki ijodi va diniy e'tiqodlar bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Shu bois, gul nomlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish nafaqat tilshunoslik, balki madaniyatshunoslik, tarjimashunoslik va etnolingvistika sohalari uchun ham dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Bugungi globallashuv sharoitida turli tillardagi madaniy birliklarni o'rganish va ularni to'g'ri talqin etish zarurati ortib bormoqda. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz tillarida ishlatiladigan gul nomlari o'ziga xos leksik-semantik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, ularning ayrimlari bir-biriga to'g'ri kelmaydi yoki turlicha konnotatsiyaga ega bo'ladi. Bu holat tarjima jarayonida va madaniy muloqotda muayyan qiyinchiliklarni yuzaga keltiradi.

Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi — o'zbek va ingliz tillarida ishlatiladigan gul nomlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish, ularning semantik, leksik va madaniy jihatdan o'xshash va farqli tomonlarini aniqlash hamda ushbu birliklarning tarjima va lingvokulturologik muammolarini yoritishdir.

1. Gul nomlarining leksik-semantik xususiyatlari

Gul nomlari har qanday tilning leksik boyligi va semantik tizimida alohida o'rin egallaydi. Ular atrof-muhitni tasvirlash, inson ruhiy olamini ifodalash, estetik zavq uyg'otish va ramziy ma'no yaratishda muhim vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. O'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi gul nomlari o'zining leksik-semantik xususiyatlari bilan bir-biridan farq qiladi, bu esa har ikki tildagi dunyoqarash va madaniyat tafovutlarini aks ettiradi.

O'zbek tilida gul nomlari ko'pincha o'zbek xalqining qadimiy e'tiqodlari, an'analari va tabiatga bo'lgan munosabatini ifodalaydi. Masalan, lola, nargis, boychechak, rayhon kabi gullar o'zbek adabiyoti va og'zaki ijodida sevgi, sadoqat, bahor, poklik kabi tushunchalar bilan bog'lanadi. "Rayhon" so'zining qo'llanishi esa nafaqat gul nomi, balki ifor, poklik, muqaddaslik kabi ma'nolarni anglatadi. Ingliz tilida esa gul nomlari ko'proq yunon-rim mitologiyasi, diniy konnotatsiyalar yoki madaniy stereotiplar asosida shakllangan. Masalan, rose (atirgul) muhabbat va ehtiros timsoli, lily (zambak) esa poklik va beg'uborlik timsoli sifatida qaraladi. Daffodil esa bahorning kelishini anglatuvchi madaniy belgi sifatida ingliz she'riyatida keng qo'llaniladi.

Har ikki tilda ayrim gul nomlari o'zaro mos kelsa-da (masalan, tulip — lola, rose — atirgul), ba'zilarining to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ekvivalentlari yo'q. Bunday hollarda ma'no tafovuti, ramziy yuklama va qo'llanilish konteksti tarjima jarayonida e'tiborga

olinishi lozim. Shuningdek, gul nomlari o'zbek va ingliz tillarida biriktirilgan semantik konnotatsiya jihatidan ham farqlanadi. Masalan, o'zbek madaniyatida atirgul — go'zallik va halollik timsoli, ingliz tilida esa ko'proq romantik muhabbat bilan bog'liq.

2. Gul nomlarining lingvokulturologik tahlili

Gul nomlari nafaqat til, balki madaniyat va urf-odatlar bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Har bir tilning o'ziga xos lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari mavjud bo'lib, ular o'zaro farq qiladi. Gul nomlarining lingvokulturologik tahlili tilshunoslikning bir qismi sifatida, til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganadi. O'zbek tilida gul nomlari ko'pincha milliy e'tiqodlar, an'analar va tabiatga bo'lgan hurmatni ifodalovchi madaniy elementlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ingliz tilida esa, gul nomlari, asosan, yevropacha romantizm va diniy qadriyatlar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ularda estetik va emotsional ma'nolar keng tarqalgan.

O'zbek va ingliz tillarida gul nomlari bo'yicha madaniy yuklamalar bir-biridan farqlanadi. Masalan, o'zbek tilida “atirgul” ko'proq go'zallik, poklik va sadoqatning ramzi sifatida qabul qilinsa, ingliz tilida esa bu gul, ayniqsa, sevgi va ehtiros bilan bog'liqdir. Shuningdek, ba'zi gullarning nomlari madaniy o'ziga xosliklarni aks ettiradi. “Lola” (tulip) o'zbek tilida bahorning keltiruvchisi bo'lsa, ingliz tilida bu gul odatda estetik va romantik tasvirlarda ishlatiladi. Lingvokulturologik tahlil gul nomlari orqali xalqning dunyoqarashi va qadriyatlarini tushunishga yordam beradi, chunki ular milliy madaniyatning ajralmas qismidir.

3. Gul nomlarining tarjima va ekvivalentlik masalalari

Tarjima jarayonida gul nomlarini to'g'ri va aniq ifodalash katta ahamiyatga ega. O'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi gul nomlarining to'g'ri tarjimasini uchun ularning semantik va madaniy konnotatsiyalarini hisobga olish zarur. Har bir til o'ziga xos leksik va semantik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgani uchun, ba'zi gul nomlarini to'g'ri tarjima qilishda qiyinchiliklar yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Gul nomlarining to'g'ri ekvivalentlarini topish yoki ular o'rtasidagi ma'no tafovutlarini aniqlash tarjima sifatini yaxshilaydi.

Masalan, ingliz tilidagi “rose” so'zi o'zbek tilida “atirgul” sifatida tarjima qilinadi, lekin ingliz tilidagi “rose” va o'zbek tilidagi “atirgul” o'rtasidagi semantik farqlarni hisobga olish zarur. Ingliz tilida “rose” ko'pincha sevgi va ehtiros ramzi sifatida ishlatiladi, o'zbek tilida esa, bu so'z, ko'proq go'zallik, poklik va sadoqat bilan bog'liqdir.

Gul nomlarini tarjima qilishda, shu bilan birga, ba'zi gul nomlarining to'g'ri ekvivalentlarini topish mushkul bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, o'zbek tilidagi “rayhon” so'zi ingliz tilida to'g'ri tarjima qilinmaydi, chunki u o'zbek madaniyatida o'ziga xos ma'no va ramziy yuklamaga ega.

XULOSA

O‘zbek va ingliz tillarida gul nomlarining qiyosiy tahlili tilshunoslik, madaniyatshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik sohalarida katta ahamiyatga ega. Gul nomlari nafaqat tilning leksik boyligini, balki xalqning dunyoqarashi, e‘tiqodlari, madaniyatiga oid chuqur ma‘nolarni aks ettiradi. Maqolada o‘zbek va ingliz tillaridagi gul nomlari orasidagi leksik, semantik va madaniy tafovutlar ko‘rsatildi va ularning tarjima jarayonidagi o‘ziga xos qiyinchiliklari yoritildi. Har ikkala tilda gullarning nomlari orqali milliy e‘tiqodlar va qadriyatlar ifodalanadi, bu esa ularning lingvokulturologik ahamiyatini yanada oshiradi.

Gul nomlarining tarjima jarayonida tilshunoslar va tarjimonlar har ikki tilning semantik va madaniy xususiyatlarini inobatga olishlari zarur. Gul nomlarining to‘g‘ri tarjimasini madaniy muloqot va muloqotning yaxshi o‘tishiga yordam beradi, bu esa o‘zaro tushunishni ta‘minlaydi.

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Cross-Cultural Analyses of the Words “Woman” and “Child” in English and Uzbek Proverbs

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Abstract: This study examines the sociocultural meanings associated with the terms "woman" and "child" that are found in Uzbek and English proverbs. The study examines a set of proverbs from both languages using a comparative framework and a corpus-based methodology in order to find recurrent themes and disparate representations. The results, which reflect underlying cultural values and historical backgrounds, show notable disparities in how these two cultures view the roles, characteristics, and societal expectations connected with women and children. By emphasizing the value of proverbs as linguistic artifacts for comprehending cultural nuances, this study advances the fields of ethnolinguistics and cross-cultural pragmatics.

Key words: Cross-cultural analyses, woman, child, social expectations, cultural nuances.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz maqollarida uchraydigan “ayol” va “bola” atamalari bilan bog'liq ijtimoiy-madaniy ma'nolar o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotda ikkala tilga oid maqollar jamlanmasi qiyosiy tahlil va korpus metodologiyasi asosida tahlil qilinadi hamda unda o'xshash va farqlanuvchi jihatlar aniqlanadi. Natijalar asosiy madaniy qadriyatlar va tarixiy omillardagi ikki madaniyatda ayollar va bolalarga nisbatan ijtimoiy rollar, xususiyatlar va munosabatlardagi aniq farqlarni ko'rsatadi. Maqollarni madaniy o'ziga xosliklarni tushunishda lingvistik artefakt sifatida baholagan holda, ushbu tadqiqot etnolingvistika va madaniyatlararo pragmatika sohalariga ilmiy hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo tahlil, ayol, bola, orzu-istak, ijtimoiy-madaniy farqlar.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании рассматриваются социокультурные значения, связанные с терминами "женщина" и "ребенок", которые встречаются в узбекских и английских пословицах. В исследовании рассматривается набор пословиц из обоих языков с использованием сравнительного подхода и корпусной методологии, чтобы выявить повторяющиеся темы и несопоставимые репрезентации. Результаты, которые отражают основополагающие культурные ценности и исторические предпосылки, показывают заметные различия в том, как эти две культуры рассматривают роли, характеристики и ожидания общества, связанные с женщинами и детьми. Подчеркивая ценность пословиц как лингвистических артефактов для понимания культурных нюансов, это исследование развивает области этнолингвистики и кросс-культурной прагматики.

Ключевые слова: Кросс-культурный анализ, женщина, ребенок, социальные ожидания, культурные нюансы.

Introduction

Proverbs provide a distinctive perspective for analyzing a society's cultural values and ideas since they are succinct statements of wisdom and customary knowledge. In addition to offering insights about gender roles, societal standards, and intergenerational relationships, they capture communal experiences. The crosscultural analysis of the terms "woman" and "child" in Uzbek and English proverbs is the main topic of this study. We search to identify the underlying cultural presumptions and social constructions connected to these ideas in Uzbek and English cultures by contrasting the semantic and pragmatic roles of these words within their respective proverb corpora.

The selection of "woman" and "child" is based on their essential functions in establishing social structures and passing down cultural traditions. We can comprehend the culturally particular views of gender, age, and social standing by looking at how these terms are utilized in proverbs. Age and gender biases in proverbs have been examined in earlier research (e.g., Mieder, 1985; Norrick, 1985). However, a comparative study of Uzbek and English proverbs is still mostly unexplored. By offering a methodical and data-driven comparison of these two different linguistic and cultural environments, this study fills this gap.

Questions for Research:

Which thematic images of "woman" and "child" predominate in English proverbs?

In Uzbek proverbs, how are "woman" and "child" portrayed thematically?

In what ways do these depictions vary across the two civilizations, and what possible historical and cultural elements influence these variations?

Materials and Methods

The proverbs of each country are different from one another, depending on the history of creation and the ways which people express in their lifestyle (Palmer, 1981). There are some similarities and differences between English and Uzbek proverbs. In this article we analyse proverbs in various ways using different methods of investigation:

1. Information Gathering
2. Data analyses
3. Stylistic
4. Comparative

The following sources were used to construct a corpus of proverbs in both English and Uzbek:

1. English:

The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs (Speake, 2015)

A Dictionary of American Proverbs (Mieder W., 1992)

Online proverb databases (e.g., The Phrase Finder)

2. Uzbek:

“O‘zbek Xalq Maqollari” (Uzbek Folk Proverbs) (various editions)

“Maqol, Matallar va Iboralar Lug’ati” (Dictionary of Proverbs, Sayings, and Idioms) (Mirzaev et al., 2017)

The initial corpus comprised approximately 500 English and 500 Uzbek proverbs. From these, a subset of proverbs containing the words “woman/women” (and their morphological variants, e.g., “wife”) and “child/children” (and their morphological variants, e.g., “son,” “daughter”) in English, and their equivalents “ayol,” “xotin,” “qiz,” “bola,” “o’g’il,” and “farzand” in Uzbek, was selected for analysis.

Data Analysis

The analysis was conducted in two stages:

Thematic Analysis

The chosen proverbs went through thematic analysis. Each one was precisely reviewed to reveal the main message and the specific manifestation of "woman" or "child." Repeated themes and patterns were perceived and categorized. For instance, themes concerning women included "domestic role," "beauty," "wisdom," and "deceit," while those related to children comprised "obedience," "inheritance," "future," and "education."

Comparative Analysis

The themes identified were then compared between the two languages. This process involved looking at how often each theme appeared in the English and Uzbek proverb collections and assessing the qualitative differences in their expression. For example, both languages might talk about the idea of a "home role,"

but what that means and what people expect from it can be very different in each language.

Results

There are some types of English proverbs that can not be translated into Uzbek directly. It means proverbs express the ethics and cultural manners of each nation by its ethimological origin. In such cases we need find proper equivalents to those proverbs in English and Uzbek.

English Proverbs

Woman

Domesticity and Marriage: A significant portion of English proverbs emphasizes women’s roles within the home and marriage.

“A good wife makes a good husband.” (“Erni er qiladigan ham xotin, qaro yer qiladigan ham”) [7]

“A woman’s place is in the home. [2]” (“Ayolni o'rni uyda”) [6]

Beauty and Virtue: Some proverbs equate female beauty with virtue, while

others caution against its deceptive nature.

“A fair face may hide a foul heart.” [1] (“Go‘zallik yomonlikni bekitadi”) [7]

Negative Stereotypes: A notable subset of proverbs perpetuates negative stereotypes about women, portraying them as gossipy, manipulative, or irrational.

“Women’s tongues are like lambs’ tails, always wagging.” [4] (“Ayolning tili uzun”) [7]

“Hell hath no fury like a woman scorned.” [2] (“Ayolning g‘azabi o‘tdan yomon”) [6]

Obedience and Discipline: Many proverbs stress the importance of children’s obedience and the need for strict discipline.

“Spare the rod and spoil the child.” [3] (“Bola boshidan”) [7]

“Children should be seen and not heard.” [7] (“Bolani tinglama, kuzat”) [7]

Future and Legacy: Children are often viewed as the embodiment of the future and a means of carrying on the family legacy.

“Children are a poor man’s riches.” [4] (“Farzand kambag‘alning boyligi”) [7]

Innocence and Vulnerability: Some proverbs highlight the innocence and vulnerability of children, emphasizing the need for their protection.

“Out of the mouths of babes and sucklings comes forth truth.” [4] (“Bola aldamaydi”) [7]

Uzbek Proverbs

Woman (Ayol, Xotin)

Family and Honor: Uzbek proverbs frequently associate women with the honor and reputation of the family.

“Ayol uyi bilan obod, er qadri bilan.” [3] (A woman is prosperous with her home, a man with his honor.) [5]

“Yaxshi xotin - uyning fayzi.” [6] (A good wife is the grace of the home.) [5]

Wisdom and Resourcefulness: Many proverbs portray women as wise, resourceful, and capable of managing household affairs effectively.

“Er xizmatda bo’lsa ham, ayol uyda bek.” [6] (Even if the husband is in service, the woman is the queen of the house.) [1]

Motherhood: The role of a mother is highly valued and often depicted as central to the family’s well-being.

“Jannat onalar oyog’i ostida.” [6] (Paradise lies at the feet of mothers.) [1]

Child (Bola, Farzand)

Continuation of Lineage: Children, particularly sons, are seen as crucial for ensuring the continuation of the family lineage.

“O‘g‘il bola - ota izidan, qiz bola - ona izidan.” [6] (A son follows his father’s path, a daughter follows her mother’s.) [5]

“Beshik to‘la bola bo‘lsin.” [6] (May your cradle be full of children.) [5]

Respect for Elders: Proverbs emphasize the importance of children respecting and obeying their elders.

“Kattaga hurmat, kichikka izzat.” [3] (Respect for elders, honor for the young.) [1]

Education and Upbringing: Uzbek proverbs place great importance on the proper education and upbringing of children.

“Yoshlikda olingan bilim toshga o'yilgan naqsh kabidir.” [3] (Knowledge acquired in youth is like an inscription carved in stone.) [5]

Discussion

Major variations between how "woman" and "kid" are portrayed in English and Uzbek proverbs are presented by the analysis. With women frequently confined to household duties and kids supposed to be obedient and well-behaved, English proverbs frequently replicate traditional gender stereotypes. Negative stereotypes are also common, especially with regarding women, even though some proverbs emphasize the good qualities of women and the innocent nature of children.

Uzbek proverbs, on the other hand, offer a more complex perspective on women, highlighting their intelligence, ingenuity, and vital role in upholding family honor. Women are not completely defined by their household responsibilities, yet motherhood is highly valued. In a comparable manner, Uzbek proverbs emphasize the significance of education and raising children properly, even as they emphasize the need of respecting elders. This shows a significant emphasis on the passing on of skills through generations.

These differences can be attributed to various cultural and historical factors:

Patriarchal Structures: Although patriarchy has historically existed in both Uzbek and English societies, its precise forms varied. Because of its Islamic and Central Asian roots, Uzbek society places a higher value on family loyalty and the common good, which frequently results in women playing a more important role in the family.

Religion: Uzbek civilization has been significantly shaped by Islam, whereas English culture has historically been influenced by Christianity. The proverbs represent the varying views of these religious traditions on gender roles and family relations.

Social and Economic History: A more distinct division of labor and the link of women with the home may have resulted from England's history of industrialization and urbanization. On the other hand, Uzbekistan's strong cultural norms and agrarian past might have encouraged a more integrated perspective on women's roles in society.

Individualism and Socialism: In general, Uzbek culture values socialism more than English culture does. In contrast to English culture, which emphasizes a higher value on individual success and independence, Uzbek proverbs place more focus on family honor and the value of children bringing on the family legacy.

Conclusion

This cross-cultural comparison of the terms "woman" and "kid" in Uzbek and English proverbs offers considerable insight concerning the sociocultural attitudes imprinted in these two languages. The results show that proverbs represent cultural values, historical settings, and societal expectations in addition to being expressions of folk wisdom. Although this study provides a first investigation of the subject, more work is required to broaden the corpus, look into additional pertinent terms (such as "man," "father," and "mother"), and examine the proverbs' diachronic development. Furthermore, examining how these proverbs are used in modern speech would offer a more thorough comprehension of their relevancy as well as their possible influence on attitudes in society.

We may further comprehend the complex interrelationships between language, culture, and cognition by continuing to analyze proverbs from a cross-cultural perspective. The current investigation demonstrates the value of philological research in revealing the complex framework of human experience as it is represented in the eternal wisdom of proverbs.

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ANALYSIS OF PROVERBS RELATED TO THE CATEGORY OF MORAL EVALUATION IN ENGLISH FOLKLORE

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Abstract

This article explores English proverbs that serve as vessels of moral assessments, thus shedding light on the ethical values, societal standards, and cultural ideals found in traditional English folklore. By categorizing and analyzing selected proverbs, the study illustrates how moral evaluations are embedded in language and culturally passed down through generations. Utilizing the theoretical perspectives of cultural linguistics and axiological linguistics, the research underscores how proverbs serve as markers of values, promoting virtues such as honesty and hard work while denouncing vices like greed and laziness.

Keywords: proverbs, moral evaluation, cultural values, English folklore, cultural linguistics, axiological linguistics, ethics in language.

В данной статье рассматриваются английские пословицы как носители моральных оценок, раскрывающие этические ценности, общественные нормы и культурные идеалы, присущие традиционному английскому фольклору. Посредством классификации и анализа отобранных пословиц исследование показывает, как моральные оценки закрепляются в языке и передаются из поколения в поколение. Опираясь на теоретические подходы культурной и аксиологической лингвистики, работа подчёркивает, что пословицы служат индикаторами ценностей, продвигая такие добродетели, как честность и трудолюбие, и осуждая такие пороки, как жадность и лень.

Ключевые слова: пословицы, моральная оценка, культурные ценности, английский фольклор, культурная лингвистика, аксиологическая лингвистика, этика в языке.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz maqollari axloqiy baholarning ifodachilari sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi hamda ular orqali an'anaviy ingliz folklorida mavjud bo'lgan axloqiy qadriyatlar, ijtimoiy me'yorlar va madaniy ideallar yoritiladi. Tanlab olingan maqollarni toifalash va tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot axloqiy baholarning til orqali qanday ifodalanishi va avloddan avlodga qanday uzatilishini ko'rsatadi. Madaniy lingvistika va aksiologik lingvistika nazariy yondashuvlariga asoslanib, maqola maqollarning qadriyat ko'rsatkichlari sifatida xizmat qilishini ta'kidlaydi — halollik va mehnatsevarlik kabi fazilatlarni targ'ib etib, ochko'zlik va dangasalik kabi illatlarni qoralaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqollar, axloqiy baholash, madaniy qadriyatlar, ingliz folklori, madaniy lingvistika, aksiologik lingvistika, til va axloq.

Introduction

Proverbs are succinct, symbolic statements that capture the knowledge and experience of the masses. They are useful markers of a community's worldview in the field of linguistic and cultural studies. Moral judgments—convictions about what is good or bad, virtuous or shameful, or right or wrong—are reflected in a large number of English proverbs. Examining these proverbs provides information about the moral

code and standards of conduct that are maintained in English-speaking cultures. With a focus on the category of moral judgment, this work utilizes the ideas of both cultural linguistics and axiological linguistics. Axiological categories aid in determining the ways in which language encodes values and anti-values. By endorsing some actions (like honesty and diligence) and denouncing others (like greed and laziness), proverbs function as axiological markers.

Linguistic Features and Cultural Functions: Moral proverbs usually encode essential ethical ideals and can be classed based on which qualities they stress. For example, proverbs like "Honesty is the best policy" and "Truth will out" emphasize the importance of candor, meaning that honesty eventually leads to positive consequences. Similarly, statements like "No pain, no gain" and "Early to bed and early to rise makes a man healthy, wealthy, and wise," which equate virtue with hard work, convey the significance of effort and personal responsibility. Proverbs that teach humility include "Pride comes before a fall" and "Empty vessels make the most noise," which warn against hubris and encourage modest behavior. Furthermore, the concepts of justice and fairness are expressed in sayings like "What goes around comes around" and "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you," which emphasise reciprocity and moral equity. Such proverbs are culturally imprinted statements of ethical standards and collective wisdom (Mieder, 2004; Norrick, 1985).

English moral proverbs' long-lasting effect stems from their succinct linguistic structure and rhetorical flair. These manifestations do more than just entertain or enlighten; they also have an educational and corrective role in society, actively creating and reinforcing ethical ideals. A variety of stylistic and structural qualities increase their effectiveness, making them memorable and convincing. Parallelism is an important aspect of moral proverbs that contributes to their memorability. Balanced constructs like "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you" promote moral reciprocity while simultaneously facilitating oral transmission via rhythm and symmetry. Similarly, antithesis and contrast are commonly used to illustrate moral argument.

Expressions such as "Better late than never" and "Easy come, easy go" convey competing behaviors or consequences, subtly guiding the audience toward the morally acceptable alternative (Norrick, 1985). These juxtapositions increase cognitive engagement while emphasizing ethical dichotomies like diligence against idleness or honesty versus deception. Another distinguishing feature of moral proverbs is their use of metaphor and symbolism, which allow abstract values to be imagined using familiar images. For example, "You reap what you sow" use an agricultural metaphor to describe the moral principle of consequence, but "Don't put all your eggs in one basket" expresses the values of caution and forethought using a tangible, everyday image (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). These metaphors anchor abstract principles in familiar

contexts, emphasizing their ethical importance. In addition to these techniques, numerous proverbs incorporate rhyme and alliteration to enhance their auditory charm. Expressions such as “Waste not, want not,” “Forgive and forget,” and “Practice makes perfect” display rhythmic consistency and sonic attractiveness, aiding in their easy memorization and transmission through generations (Mieder, 2004). The musical quality of these proverbs ensures they endure and circulate within oral traditions.

Apart from their linguistic grace, moral proverbs serve as educational tools in everyday life. They are often utilized in informal learning environments, especially within families, where older generations impart wisdom via succinct phrases like “Cleanliness is next to godliness” or “If you can't say anything nice, don't say anything at all.” In classrooms, teachers may reference sayings like “Hard work pays off” or “Cheaters never prosper” to promote discipline and ethical behavior. Proverbs also fulfill a regulatory role by reinforcing socially acceptable behavior. They promote adherence to shared values—for instance, “Well begun is half done” endorses the principle of initiative, while “The early bird catches the worm” celebrates punctuality and ambition. At the same time, they deter social deviance; expressions such as “He who lies down with dogs shall rise with fleas” or “Idle hands are the devil's workshop” warn against immoral company and laziness, associating them with personal and moral decline (Taylor, 1931). In this regard, proverbs act as a kind of “folk law,” providing moral guidance without formal enforcement. The **oral tradition** is central to the cultural power of proverbs. Especially in traditional or pre-literate communities, proverbs function as key vehicles for transmitting moral knowledge across generations. They are embedded in fables and stories—such as Aesop's Fables—where the moral is often encapsulated in a proverbial form. Even in modern contexts, children encounter moral proverbs in nursery rhymes and everyday conversations with elders, preserving these expressions as part of a shared moral heritage.

In modern society, moral proverbs are still quite significant and continue to manifest in different modes of communication. Politicians utilize them to foster unity and strength, as exemplified by the phrase “United we stand, divided we fall.” Self-help publications adapt these sayings to encourage resilience and self-confidence, offering variations such as “What doesn't kill you makes you stronger.” Popular culture, through movies, music, and advertisements, frequently appropriates proverbial wisdom, even if sometimes modified, to resonate with the audience. Phrases like “Actions speak louder than words” are widely recognized today, underscoring values like accountability and integrity.

Thus, moral proverbs exist at the crossroads of language, culture, and ethics. Their artistic form enhances their educational role, enabling them to influence moral awareness while maintaining cultural identity.

A notable number of English proverbs also embody ideals linked to the Protestant work ethic, a concept thoroughly explored by Max Weber in *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism* (1905/2002). According to Weber, the Protestant focus on discipline, labor, and thriftiness significantly influenced the moral outlook in Anglo-American society. Sayings like “Early to bed and early to rise makes a man healthy, wealthy, and wise,” and “God helps those who help themselves” encapsulate this philosophy, highlighting self-discipline, responsibility, and the moral duty to contribute constructively to society, thereby reinforcing the notion that ethical virtue and worldly success are interconnected.

Additionally, the emphasis on justice and equity in English moral proverbs—illustrated by phrases such as “What goes around comes around” and “Do unto others as you would have them do unto you”—indicates an underlying cultural value placed on reciprocity and moral balance. These sayings suggest that ethical conduct is governed by inherent or divine principles of equilibrium and retribution. As scholars like Norrick (1985) and Taylor (1931) have pointed out, these proverbs often function as informal tools for social regulation, reinforcing accepted standards of behavior without relying on formal institutional enforcement. An additional significant feature of English moral proverbs is their focus on individual morality, placing a higher value on personal responsibility than on communal duty. This perspective is evident in sayings such as “You made your bed, now lie in it” and “Every man for himself,” which highlight the importance of individual accountability and the repercussions of personal decisions. While these expressions uphold the value of moral independence, they also endorse an ethical framework based on personal agency rather than communal reliance. This is consistent with wider Western philosophical traditions that emphasize individual rights and moral reasoning, contrasting with the more collectivist ethical systems found in other cultures (Hofstede, 2001).

Nevertheless, even with their emphasis on individualism, English proverbs do not completely overlook the social aspect of morality. They frequently stress the importance of treating others with fairness and respect, as illustrated by the Golden Rule or the caution that “He who lies down with dogs shall rise with fleas.” These proverbs acknowledge that one's moral decisions affect others and that social harmony relies on mutual ethical behavior. Therefore, proverbs serve both as moral guides and cultural symbols, conveying values that reconcile personal integrity with civic duty (Dundes, 1981; Mieder, 2004).

In summary, the collection of English proverbs provides insightful perspectives on the moral fabric of English-speaking communities. These proverbs are not merely linguistic oddities; they are influential instruments for encoding and passing down ethical guidelines and cultural ideals through the ages. Acting as indicators of values, they categorize actions and behaviors into desirable and undesirable, promoting virtues

such as honesty, hard work, and fairness while discouraging faults like greed, laziness, and deceit. The potency of these moral proverbs is heightened by their unique linguistic attributes. Features such as parallel structure, contrasting ideas, metaphor, and rhyme enhance their memorability and persuasive influence, ensuring their ongoing significance in both spoken and written forms. Beyond their aesthetic charm, these proverbs are vital in shaping social behavior, serving dual roles as educational tools and social control mechanisms. While numerous English proverbs highlight the significance of personal ethics and responsibilities, indicating a cultural focus on individualism, they also acknowledge the social aspect of morality. Proverbs often emphasize the importance of treating others justly and respectfully, recognizing that individual behaviors impact the community, and social harmony relies on shared ethical conduct. Ultimately, English moral proverbs function both as practical resources for navigating daily life and as lasting cultural symbols. They encapsulate the delicate equilibrium between personal integrity values and civic responsibility requirements, presenting a rich array of ethical insights that continue to resonate in English-speaking societies.

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Miqdor kategoriyasi haqida umumiy ma'lumot

Mamadjanova Munojatxon Najmiddinovna

katta o'qituvchi, Qo'qonDU

Najmiddinova Odinaxo Shuhratjon qizi

Qo'qonDU talabasi

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada miqdor kategoriyasi va son turkumining xususiyatlari tadqiq etiladi. Miqdor anglatuvchi fonetik, morfologik, leksik va sintaktik vositalar ko'rib chiqilgan. Sonlar, ularning nutqdagi ma'nolariga katta e'tibor qaratilgan. Sonning o'ziga xos jihatlari miqdoriy aloqalarni aks ettiruvchi boshqa turkumlarni qiyoslash orqali ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar

Miqdor, son, badiiy matn, mantiqiy-semantik kategoriya, miqdoriylik va kvantitativlik.

Аннотация.

В настоящей статье исследуется языковая категория количества, сочетательные свойства числительных. Рассматриваются различные средства обозначения количества: фонетические, морфологические, лексические и синтаксические. Большое место отведено числительным, их значениям в речи. Специфика числительного раскрывается посредством анализа других частей речи, которые также выражают количественные отношения.

Ключевые слова

Количество, числительное, художественный текст, логико-семантическая категория, количественность и квантитативность.

Annotation

In this article, we study the language category of quantity, the combining properties of numerals. Various means of denoting the number are considered: phonetic, morphological, lexical and syntactic. A great place is given to numerals, their values in speech. The specifics of the numerals are revealed through the analysis of other parts of speech, which also express quantitative relationships.

Keywords

Quantity, numeral, literary text, logical-semantic category, quantity and quantit.

Tilshunoslar miqdor kategoriyasini yuzaga chiqaruvchi vositalari, miqdoriylik ma'nolari bilan bog'liq muammolarni o'rganganlar. Bunda "miqdor" bilan terminologik yaqin tushunchalar sifatida quyidagilar ajratib ko'rsatilgan: miqdor, miqdoriylik va kvantitativlik. Miqdor deyilganda sanalish va o'lchanish imkoniyati tushuniladi, miqdoriylik – miqdor kategoriyasiga asoslangan xususiyatdir, kvantitativlik esa turli sathlarda miqdoriylik mazmuniga ega bo'lgan tushunchalar kompleksi haqida tasavvurni yuzaga chiqaruvchi mantiqiy-semantik kategoriya hisoblanadi. Miqdoriylik mazmuni miqdor, son, ko'plik, qisqalik kabilarni o'z ichiga oladi. Shuningdek, kvantitativlik ma'nosi tartib, o'lchov parametrlariga aloqador tushunchalarni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

O'zbek tilini davlat tili sifatida mavqeiini kuchaytirish, uning boy leksikoni va o'ziga xos jihatlarini o'rganishga e'tibor kuchaydi, maktablarda va oliy o'quv yurtlarida ona tili o'qitish o'zgacha sifatli bosqichga ko'tarildi. Ona tilimizning xalqimiz mentaliteti bilan bog'liq jihatlarini, boshqa tillarda kuzatilmaydigan spetsifik qirralarini ko'rsatuvchi belgilardan biri bu kvantitativlik (miqdor)dir.

Miqdor kategoriyasi "sifat" kategoriyasi kabi borliqning umumiy xossalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Til va falsafa aloqadorligini izchil tadqiq etgan olim V.Z.Panfilovning yozishicha, mazmuniy miqdor kategoriyasi ob'ektiv olamning miqdoriy aniqligi in'ikosi natijasidir.⁸⁴ Til va tafakkur dialektik aloqadorlikda bo'lgani uchun barcha asosiy mazmuniy kategoriyalar, xususan, miqdor kategoriyasi ham tilda o'z aksini topadi.

Mavjud tadqiqotlarda miqdoriy munosabatlarning ifodalanishi uch konstant-universal ma'nolar asosida shakllanadi: 1) aniq (ob'ektiv) miqdor ma'nosi, bunda miqdor son yoki birlik, ikkilik ma'nolarini bildiruvchi substantiv ifodalar yordamida ifodalanadi: *ikki, olti, (bir) kitob, scales (tarazi – ikki pallasi bo'lgani uchun), glasses (ko'zoynak – ikki oynasi bo'lgani uchun)* kabi; 2) aniqlashtirilgan (sub'ektiv) miqdor ma'nosi, bunda **kvantifikatorlar** yordamga keladi: *many - ko'plab, several - bir qancha, some/few - bir nechta*; 3) mavhum miqdor ma'nosi morfemalar yordamida ifodalanadi: ingliz tilida *-s*, rus tilida *-bi* kabi.¹

Ushbu bo'linishdan ko'rinib turibdiki, miqdor kategoriyasining tilda aks etishi turlicha bo'lib, vositalari ham rang-barang. O'zbek tilida miqdor ma'nosining yuzaga chiqishini ta'minlovchi fonetik, leksik va grammatik vositalar ham talaygina. Ayniqsa, morfologik sathda so'z turkumlari (ot, sifat, son, olmosh, fe'l, ravish) yordamida miqdor ma'nosining ifodalanishi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Aniq miqdor ma'nosi har bir so'z turkumida mavjud. Buni quyidagi misollar tasdiqlaydi:

- 1) otlarda: juft, egizak, ikkilik, ko'plik, to'rtlik, dekada (o'n kunlik);
- 2) sifatlarda: yagona, yolg'iz, qo'sh;
- 3) sonlarda: bir, ikki, uch;
- 4) olmoshlarda: har bir, hamma, hech bir;

Noaniq miqdor ma'nosining ifodalanishi *ko'p, bir qancha, oz, kam, bir oz* kabi sub'ektiv baho hisobiga aniqlashtiruvchi kvantifikatorlar yordamida yoki so'zning semantik strukturasi tarkibiga singib ketgan jamlik, umumiylik ma'nosini yuzaga chiqaruvchi aniqlashtiruvchi unsurlar (*oila, partiya, kompaniya, guruh, to'da, pada, komanda*) yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

⁸⁴ Панфилов В.З. Философские проблемы языкознания. – М.: Наука, 1977. -С.158.

² Кошечая И.Г. К проблеме знака и значения в языке. – М.: Просвещение, 1976. -С.10.

Tilda noaniq ko'plik ma'nosi ot, olmosh va fe'llardagi son grammatik kategoriyasi asosida yuzaga chiqadi. Ushbu kategoriyaning mohiyati "bir – birdan ko'p" oppozitsiyasida namoyon bo'ladi, bunda birinchi shakl yagonalik, yakkalik ma'nosini, ikkinchi shakl esa noaniq ko'plik ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Biroq shu o'rinda alohida ta'kidlash joizki, fe'lda son grammatik shakli harakat miqdorini ifodalamaydi (aslida kategorial ma'nosiga muvofiq holda bo'lishi kerak), balki harakat ishtirokchilarining sonini (grammatik sub'ekt) ko'rsatadi. Demak, fe'llardagi son grammatik shakli "vositachilik" xarakteriga ega bo'ladi va ot yoki olmosh orqali ifodalangan miqdor ma'nosini ikkilantiradi. Masalan: ***Sen** kitob o'qiy**san**. **Biz** ko'cha bo'ylab yuguryap**miz***. Xuddi shunday miqdor ma'nosining "qo'shaloqlanishi", "ikkilanishi" rus tilida ham mavjud, lekin ingliz tili materialida III shaxs birlik shaklini (***He** speaks English fluently – U inglizchada ravon gapiradi*) hisobga olmaganda kuzatilmaydi. O'zbek tilida ayrim hollarda ushbu holat o'ziga xos xarakterga ega holda ifodalanadi. Ya'ni miqdor ma'nosi fe'lda ikki marta ikkilanadi, batizmatik holda qo'llanadi, buni "**lingvistik unikaliya**" sifatida baholash mumkin: *Il**timos** suyan**mangiz**, O'tir**ingiz*** kabi ifodalarda - (i)ng hamda -iz shakllari qo'shaloq holda ishlatilgan.

Fe'ldagi son ma'nosining o'ziga xosligini alohida ta'kidlab I.G.Koshevaya o'zining "Проблемы языкознания и теории английского языка" ("Tilshunoslik muammolari va ingliz tili nazariyasi") kitobida shunday yozadi: "...fe'llarda birlik va ko'plik sonning farqi jarayonning tub mohiyatiga tegishlidir. Ular orasidagi tafovutni birlik sondagi aniqlik va ko'plik sondagi mavhumlik bilan belgilash mumkin".¹ Garchi fe'llardagi son grammatik kategoriyasi vositachilik xarakteriga ega bo'lsa ham, harakat bajaruvchilarining sonidan tashqari fe'lning o'zi ham miqdor ma'nosini yuzaga chiqishini ta'minlovchi leksik va grammatik xususiyatlarga ham ega. Jumladan, harakatning makon-zamon sig'imidagi cheklanganlik va cheklanmaganlik asosidagi zidlanishi asosida miqdor ma'nosi sezilib turadi: olib kelmoq - keltirmoq; qochmoq - yugurmoq; kelmoq - ketmoq. Harakatda sub'ekt ishtirokining kvantitativ ifodalanishi, ayniqsa, fe'llarda nisbat kategoriyasida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. O'zbek tili misolida boshqa tillarga qaraganda nisbat kategoriyasining keng rivojlanganligi² va uni yuzaga chiqaruvchi grammatik shakllarga boyligi fe'l tizimida kvantitativlikning yorqinroq namoyon bo'lishini ko'rsatadi. O'zbek tilidagi 5 nisbat ish-harakt sub'ekti va ob'ektining kvantitativ belgi asosida zidlanishini belgilaydi:

1. Aniq nisbatda sub'ekt va ob'ekt miqdori teng bo'ladi: *Azimjon xat yozyapti*.

2. O'zlik nisbatida sub'ekt ham, ob'ekt ham yagona bo'ladi: *Azimjon to'garakka yozildi*.

¹ Кошечая И.Г. Проблемы языкознания и теории английского языка. – М.: Просвещение, 1976. – С.53.

² Бу ҳақида қаранг: Ғулломов А.Ғ. Фель. – Тошкент, 1954; Ҳожиёв А. Фель. – Тошкент, 1978.

3. Majhul nisbatda sub'ekt qatnashmaydi, ob'ekt ifodalanadi, bunda sub'ek va ob'ekt kvantifikatsiyasi noteng bo'ladi: *Xatlar yozildi.*

1. Birgalik nisbatida sub'ektlar ko'payadi, lekin miqdor noaniq, mavhum bo'ladi: *Bolalar insho yozishyapti.*

2. Orttirma nisbatda sub'ektlar miqdori eng kamida bittaga ortadi: *U inglizcha xatni birovga yozdirdi.*

O'zbek tilida fe'llarda miqdor ma'nosi leksik usul yordamida ham ifodalanishi mumkin, lekin ot va sifatlardan farqli ravishda fe'llar aniq ko'plik ma'nosini anglatish xususiyatiga ega emas. *Birlashtirmoq, juftlashtirmoq, ikkilantirmoq* kabi ayrim yasama fe'llarda o'zakdagi aniq miqdor semasi butun fe'lga tegishli bo'lib qoladi. Bu istisnoli holat sifatida baholanadi. Leksik yo'l bilan miqdor ma'nosining ifodalanishi son kategoriyasiga qaraganda aniqroq va ravshanroq yuzaga chiqadi. Bu holatda fe'l miqdorning o'zini nomlamaydi, balki kattalashish va kichayish shkalasi asosida kvantitativ (miqdoriy) munosabatlarning dinamikasini o'ziga xos tarzda aks ettiradi. Shunga asosan fe'llarni ikki guruhga ajratish mumkin:

1. Kattalashishga tomon miqdoriy o'zgarishni ko'rsatuvchi fe'llar: *qo'shmoq, ko'paytirmoq, oshirmoq, kuchaytirmoq, ko'tarmoq, ko'tarilmoq, intilmoq, yugurmoq, sakramoq, yiriklashtirmoq, kengaytirmoq* kabi.

2. Kichrayishga tomon miqdoriy o'zgarishni ifodalovchi fe'llar: *ayirmoq, kamaytirmoq, pasaymoq, susaymoq, kesmoq, tushmoq, ozaymoq* kabi.

Keltirilgan misollardan ko'rinib turibdiki, ularda kvantitativ dinamika gradual zidlanish asosida ifodalanmoqda: bir me'yorda ko'tarilish va tushish (kuchaymoq – susaymoq; rivojlanmoq – tanazzulga yuz tutmoq) yoki bir tomondan ikkinchi tomonga keskin o'zgarish (sakramoq – tushmoq; ko'tarilmoq – tushmoq). Fe'llardagi bunday xususiyat miqdoriy munosabatlar dinamikasini farqlashda, til birliklarining kvantitativ belgi asosida zidlanishini mohiyatan tushunishda alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Demak, miqdor kategoriyasining tilda ifodalanishi leksik va grammatik vositalar yordamida yuzaga chiqadigan aniq va noaniq kvantifikatsiyani o'z ichiga oladi. O'zbek tilida aniq miqdor leksik vositalar yordamida ifodalanadi; noaniq miqdor esa ham leksik, ham grammatik usul yordamida ifodalanadi. O'zbek tilida fe'llarda kvantitativlikning ifodalanishi o'ziga xos jihatlar bilan ajralib turadi va yuqorida tahlil etilgan ayrim nuqtalar “**lingvistik unikalija**” darajasiga ko'tarilgan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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Ikki tillilik va uning metalingvistik tushunchalarga ta'siri

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ikki tillilik va uning metalingvistik ongga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Metalingvistik ong, til strukturalarini anglash va manipulyatsiya qilish qobiliyatidir, ikki tillilik, ya'ni bilingvizmning bu jarayonni qanday rivojlantirishi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ikki tilli bolalar grammatika, leksika va sintaksis kabi tilning turli jihatlarini boshqarish va o'zlashtirishda ba'zan monolingvist (bir tilli) bolalarga qaraganda ustunlikka ega. Biroq, metalingvistik tushunchaning rivojlanishiga tildagi kombinatsiyalar va mahorat darajasi kabi omillar ta'sir qiladi. Ikkita tilni yaxshi o'rgangan bolalar boshqa tildagi tizimlarni o'rganish jarayonida metalingvistik ongdan samarali foydalanadilar.

Kalit so'zlar: Metalingvistik ong, **bilingvizm**, ikki tillilik, til tipi, grammatika, leksika, sintaksis, til kombinatsiyasi, metalingvistik funktsiyalar.

Annotation: This study analyzes bilingualism and its effect on metalinguistic awareness. Metalinguistic awareness is the ability to understand and manipulate language structures, and the paper discusses how bilingualism develops this process. Research shows that bilingual children sometimes have an advantage over monolingual children in managing and acquiring various aspects of language, such as grammar, lexicon, and syntax. However, factors like language combinations and proficiency levels influence the development of metalinguistic awareness. Children who are proficient in two languages effectively use metalinguistic awareness in learning new language systems.

Keywords: Metalinguistic awareness, bilingualism, language typology, inhibition, selective attention, grammar, lexical awareness, syntactic awareness, language combination, metalinguistic functions.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании анализируется двуязычие и его влияние на метаязыковое сознание. Метаязыковое сознание — это способность понимать и манипулировать языковыми структурами, и в работе рассматривается, как двуязычие развивает этот процесс. Исследования показывают, что двуязычные дети иногда имеют преимущество перед монолингвами в управлении и освоении различных аспектов языка, таких как грамматика, лексика и синтаксис. Однако на развитие метаязыкового сознания влияют такие факторы, как языковые комбинации и уровень владения языками. Дети, хорошо владеющие двумя языками, эффективно используют метаязыковое сознание при изучении новых языковых систем.

Ключевые слова: Метаязыковое сознание, двуязычие, типология языка, ингибирование, избирательное внимание, грамматика, лексическое сознание, синтаксическое сознание, языковая комбинация, метаязыковые функции.

Kirish

Bilingvizm, ikki tillilikni o'rganishda muhim bo'lgan yana bir jihat — bu uning metalingvistik ongga ta'siridir. Metakognitsiyaning kichik toifasi sifatida (Roberts, 2011), metalingvistik bilim ongli bilishni nazorat qilishdan foydalanadi, bu esa ongsiz ravishda bilim olishdan farq qiladi. Bu tushunchaning turli talqinlariga qaramay, metalingvistik ong quyidagicha ta'riflanadi: “Og'zaki tilning strukturaviy xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish va ularni o'zgartira olish qobiliyati, ya'ni tilni shunchaki tushunish va gaplar tuzish uchun emas, balki uni tafakkur ob'ekti sifatida ko'ra olish”dir. (Tunmer & Herriman, 1984, 12-bet). Tilning bu xususiyatlari fonologiya, sintaksis, morfologiya, fraza tuzilishi, semantika, pragmatika, matn turlari va ularning tuzilmalari haqidagi bilim hamda suhbat qoidalari kabi sohalarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin.

Metalingvistik ong shaxsga tilning ma'nosini uni o'z ichiga olgan kontekstdan ajratib olish imkonini beradi. Metatilingaviy ongga misol sifatida ma'no va shakllarni ajrata olish, til komponentlarini farqlay olish, noaniqlikni aniqlash va grammatik shakllar hamda tuzilmalar qo'llanilishini tushunish kabilar keltiriladi (De Angelis, 2007). Bolalar metalingvistik ongni uch bosqichda rivojlantiradilar: bilvosita bilim, epilingvistik bilim va nihoyat aniq (ongli) bilim. Metalingvistik ong erta bolalik davrida, maktabgacha yoshda paydo bo'ladi va bolalik davomida rivojlanadi, savod chiqarish jarayonida esa keskin sakrash kuzatiladi.

Metalingvistik ong boshqa bir qancha psixologik jarayonlar, xususan, diqqat yoki sezish bilan kesishadi, biroq ular o'zaro farqlanadi. Diqqat (yoki sezish) — bu ongga kirishni boshqaruvchi mexanizmdir. Metatilingaviy ong shuningdek, til qobiliyati bilan ham bog'liq. Garchi bu tushuncha biroz tortishuvli bo'lsa-da, chet tilini o'rganish qobiliyati “chet tilini o'rganishni yengillashtiruvchi asosiy qobiliyatlar majmui” sifatida ta'riflanishi mumkin (Carroll & Sapon, 1959, 14-bet). Metalingvistik

ong va til qobiliyati orasidagi o'xshashlik turli til qobiliyati testlari orqali namoyon bo'ladi. Bu o'xshashlikni tilga olish shart, chunki metalingvistik ong chet tilini o'rganishni yengillashtirishda markaziy element bo'lib ko'rinadi.

Barcha bolalar metalingvistik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirsa-da, ikki tilli bolalarning metalingvistik ongi tadqiqotchilar uchun alohida qiziqish uyg'otgan va bu borada uzoq tarixga ega. Nazariy farazga ko'ra, ikki tillilar ikki tildagi kognitiv talablarga duch kelganliklari sababli til haqida qo'shimcha ong hosil qiladilar. Ikki tildagi talablarni boshqarar ekanlar, ikki tilli bolalar tildagi tuzilmalarga nisbatan tahliliy yondashuvni o'zlashtiradilar va tilni o'ziga xos ob'ekt sifatida ko'ra boshlaydilar, bu esa kuchaygan metalingvistik ongga olib keladi. Bu ong yangi topshiriqlarni bajarishda yoki yangi til kodiga murojaat qilishda ishga solinishi mumkin. Bir xil fikrni turli tillarda ifodalash qobiliyatiga ega bo'lgan ikki tilli bola o'z tilini boshqa tizimlar orasidagi yagona tizim sifatida ko'ra oladi, til hodisalarini umumiyroq toifalar ostida tahlil qiladi va bu esa o'zining til bilan bog'liq amallarini anglashiga olib keladi. Ikki tilning ichkilashtirilishini murakkabroq, yaxshi jihozlangan aqliy hisob-kitob tizimiga olib keladi, deb hisoblaydi. Bu esa ikki tillilarga til tizimlari qoidalarini osonroq boshqarish imkonini beradi. Metalingvistik ong ijroiylar funksiyalarning, ayniqsa, inhibitsiya (to'sish) funksiyasining ishga solinishini ham talab qiladi, chunki bu ayrim til jihatlarini bostirishni talab qiladi. Shuning uchun, ma'lum darajada metalingvistik ong tushunchasi ijroiylar funksiyalar bilan ustma-ust keladi va ular bilan birgalikda faoliyat ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, metalingvistik ong tillar orasida o'zaro ko'chishi mumkinligi ham ilgari surilgan, garchi bu ko'chishning aniq tabiati hali noma'lum bo'lsa ham (Verhoeven, 2007).

Kuchli nazariy farazlarga qaramay, empirik tadqiqotlar ikki tilli bolalarning metalingvistik ongi borasida bir xil natijalarni bermaydi. Metalingvistik ong ko'pincha yagona tushuncha sifatida talqin qilinadi va tadqiqotda shu tarzda qo'llaniladi, biroq odatda u bir nechta kichik toifalarga ajratiladi (Roberts, 2011). Bu kichik tadqiqot ishimizda biz fonologik, sintaktik va leksik ong bo'yicha muhokamani davom ettiramiz. Metalingvistik ongning eng ko'p o'rganilgan jihati — bu fonologik ong bo'lib, u bo'g'inlar, bosh tovushlar, ohang bo'laklari va fonemalarni boshqarish qobiliyatini anglatadi. Juda ko'plab empirik tadqiqotlarga qaramay, ikki tillilik va fonologik ong o'rtasida izchil ijobiy bog'liqlik aniqlanmagan. Bog'chada ikki tillilarda fonologik ong yuqoriroq bo'lib tuyuladi, biroq bu ustunlik birinchi sinfga kelib yo'qoladi. Kattaroq yoshdagi bolalarda ba'zi tadqiqotlar ikki tillilar fonologik ongi yuqoriligini aniqlagan (Campbell & Sais, 1995; Eviator & Ibrahim, 2000), boshqalari esa bir tilli va ikki tilli guruhlar o'rtasida hech qanday farq topmagan (Bialystok, Majumder, & Martin, 2003).

Aksincha, metalingvistik ongning boshqa jihatlarida, xususan, selektiv e'tiborni talab qiladigan jihatlarida ikki tillilarda kuchaygan ong borligiga oid

tadqiqotlar orasida ko'proq yakdillik mavjud. Sintaktik ong – grammatik xatolarni aniqlash va to'g'rilash, noaniqlikni aniqlash va izohlar yaratishni talab qiluvchi topshiriqlar orqali baholangan – ikki tilli ishtirokchilar orasida kuchliroq ekani aniqlangan. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ikki tillilar grammatik xatolarni, ayniqsa “Olmalar butada o'sadi” kabi mazmunsiz gaplar berilganida, aniqlash va to'g'rilash qobiliyatiga ega. Xuddi shuningdek, ikki tillilar leksik ong borasida ham ustunlikka ega ekani aniqlangan. Leksik ong so'z va uning ob'ekti (ko'rsatayotgan narsa)ni ajrata olish qobiliyati sifatida ta'riflanadi. Sintaktik va leksik ong holatlarida topshiriq tilning alohida jihatlarini ajratish va ularni qayta tashkil qilishni talab qiladi, bu esa selektiv e'tiborni kuchliroq nazorat qilish zaruratini tug'diradi (Bialystok, 1992; 2001).

Ikki tilli bolalarda metalingvistik ongga ta'sir qiluvchi bir nechta omillar aniqlangan, xususan, ikki tillilikdagi mahorat darajasi va til tiplari shular jumlasidan hisoblanadi. Yuqori darajadagi ikki tillilik kuchliroq metatilingaviy ko'nikmalar bilan bog'liq. Nazariy faraz shundan iboratki, metatilingaviy ongga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi uchun har ikkala tilda ma'lum bir mahorat darajasiga erishish zarur. Til resurslari kengroq bo'lgan muvozanatli ikki tillilar ilgari o'zlashtirilgan tuzilmalar (masalan, grammatika, pragmatika, leksika, talaffuz va imlo)dan foydalanib, yangi til tizimini o'rganishda ulardan foydalanishlari mumkin. Bu til o'tkazilishi, ya'ni ilgari o'rganilgan resurslarga asoslanib yangi til tuzilmalarini o'zlashtirish qobiliyati bilan solishtirilishi mumkin. Ispancha-inglizcha ikki tilli bolalarni o'rgangan Galambos va Hakuta kabi tilshunos olimlar ham til ko'nikmasi metalingvistik ongga ta'sir ko'rsatishini aniqlagan. Xuddi shuningdek, Rauch va hamkorlari yuqori darajadagi ikki tillilar (ya'ni to'liq savodli) qisman ikki tillilar va bir tilli tengdoshlariga nisbatan sezilarli ustunlikka ega ekanligini topgan. Biroq, bu ustunlik shaxsiy fon xususiyatlari – ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy holat, jins, umumiy kognitiv qobiliyatlar va maktab yo'nalishi – hisobga olinganda yo'qoladi. Yuqoridagi natijalardan farqli ravishda, ikkinchi tilga atigi olti oy ta'sirda bo'lgan cheklangan darajadagi ikki tillilar ham leksik ong borasida bir tilli tengdoshlaridan ustun bo'lishgan.

Bundan tashqari, til tiplari ham metatilingvistik ongning rivojlanishiga ta'sir qilishi bir qator tilshunos olimlar tadqiqotlarida ko'rinadi (Bialystok, 2006b). Ba'zi til guruhlari va til kombinatsiyalari metalingvistik ongning rivojlanishini boshqalarga qaraganda yaxshiroq qo'llab-quvvatlashi taxmin qilinadi. Masalan, Barac va Bialystok (2012) ispancha-inglizcha, fransuzcha-inglizcha, xitoycha-inglizcha va inglizcha bir tilli bolalarning metatilingaviy ongini baholagan. Ispancha-inglizcha ikki tillilari boshqa ikki tilli guruhlar va bir tilli guruhni sezilarli darajada ortda qoldirishgan. Mualliflar metatilingaviy ong tilning ko'proq strukturaviy o'xshashliklariga ega bo'lgan tillar (masalan, fransuzcha va inglizcha) o'rtasida ko'proq o'tkazilishi mumkinligini, kam yoki umuman strukturaviy o'xshashliklari bo'lmagan tillar

(masalan, xitoycha va inglizcha) o'rtasida esa bu o'tkazilishning kamroq bo'lishini yakuniy xulosaga kelishgan.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ijro etuvchi funksiyalarni o'rganish bilan solishtirganda natijalar kamroq kuchli va izchil bo'lsa-da, ikki tillilar ba'zi metalingvistik topshiriqlarda, xususan inhibisiya va selektiv e'tibor talab qiladigan topshiriqlarda ustunlikka ega ekanligi aniqlangan. Biroq boshqa omillar, masalan, til kombinatsiyalari va mahorat darajasi, bu aloqaga ta'sir qilishi mumkin. Metalingvistik ongning yuqori darajalari va ilgari muhokama qilingan kognitiv jarayonlardagi farqlar ikki tillining yangi tilni o'rganish qobiliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashini taklif qilingan. Keyingi tadqiqotlarimiz davomida aynan nega ikki tillilarda aniqlangan bu kuchaygan mexanizmlar muvaffaqiyatli chet tilini o'rganishni qo'llab-quvvatlashini mavzusiga alohida to'xtalishni maqsad qilganmiz.

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COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. This article explores and compares communication strategies used by speakers of English and Uzbek, with a focus on how cultural norms, discourse conventions, and linguistic structures shape verbal and non-verbal interaction. It draws from pragmatic and sociolinguistic theories to analyze achievement and reduction strategies, indirectness, politeness, and cultural values. The paper highlights key differences and similarities in the strategic use of language and emphasizes implications for language learners, educators, and cross-cultural communicators.

Keywords: Communication strategies, English, Uzbek, pragmatics, politeness, intercultural communication, second language acquisition.

Аннотация. В этой статье изучаются и сравниваются стратегии коммуникации, используемые носителями английского и узбекского языков, с акцентом на то, как культурные нормы, дискурсивные соглашения и языковые структуры формируют вербальное и невербальное взаимодействие. Она опирается на прагматические и социолингвистические теории для анализа стратегий достижения и сокращения, косвенности, вежливости и культурных ценностей. В статье подчеркиваются ключевые различия и сходства в стратегическом использовании языка и подчеркиваются последствия для изучающих язык, педагогов и кросс-культурных коммуникаторов. **Ключевые слова:** стратегии коммуникации, английский, узбекский, прагматика, вежливость, межкультурная коммуникация, освоение второго языка.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida so'zlashuvchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan muloqot strategiyalari o'rganiladi va taqqoslanadi, bunda asosiy e'tibor madaniy me'yorlar, nutq konventsiyalari va lingvistik tuzilmalar og'zaki va noverbal o'zaro ta'sirni qanday shakllantirishiga qaratilgan. U yutuq va kamaytirish strategiyalarini, bilvositalik, xushmuomalalik va madaniy qadriyatlarni tahlil qilish uchun pragmatik va sotsiolingvistik nazariyalardan foydalanadi. Maqolada tildan strategik foydalanishning asosiy farqlari va o'xshashliklari ta'kidlangan va til o'rganuvchilar, o'qituvchilar va madaniyatlararo muloqotchilar uchun ta'sirlarga urg'u berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Muloqot strategiyalari, ingliz, o'zbek, pragmatik, xushmuomalalik, madaniyatlararo muloqot, ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish.

Communication strategies are essential tools in both first and second language interactions, enabling speakers to overcome communicative challenges and express themselves effectively. This article examines and compares the use of communication strategies in English and Uzbek languages, drawing on sociolinguistic and pragmatic frameworks. It highlights how cultural values, discourse norms, and linguistic structures influence the choice and execution of these strategies. The study aims to support language learners, educators, and researchers in understanding the cross-

cultural nuances that impact verbal and non-verbal communication. Communication is not just about linguistic competence but also about the ability to navigate social interaction effectively. In both English and Uzbek, speakers use communication strategies to manage misunderstandings, compensate for vocabulary gaps, and maintain interpersonal relationships. However, the strategies differ based on language structure, social conventions, and cultural expectations. This paper explores the similarities and differences in communication strategies between English and Uzbek, with implications for language learning and intercultural understanding.

Communication strategies are defined as techniques used by speakers to avoid communication breakdowns when faced with difficulties in expressing or understanding messages. Tarone (1980) and Faerch & Kasper (1983) distinguish between:

- Achievement strategies: attempts to continue communication through paraphrasing, code-switching, or approximation.

- Reduction strategies: avoiding problematic topics or abandoning the message.

Communication strategies are particularly prominent in second-language contexts but are also present in native speaker interactions.

English Communication Strategies

In English, communication strategies are typically influenced by the language's emphasis on explicitness, individualism, and efficiency. Some key strategies include:

- Paraphrasing: "It's a thing you use to fix clothes" instead of "needle."

- Stalling or hesitation devices: "Let me see...", "How can I say this..."

- Repetition and clarification: Repeating or rephrasing when misunderstood.

- Politeness hedges: "I might be wrong, but...", "Would you mind if...?"

English speakers often use direct refusals softened by hedges, and feedback cues like "uh-huh", "right", and "I see" to show attention and involvement.

Uzbek Communication Strategies

Uzbek communication strategies reflect a collectivist and high-context culture, where harmony, respect for elders, and social hierarchy are crucial. Common strategies include:

- Indirectness and euphemisms: Avoiding direct "no" in favor of expressions like "Balki boshqa safar" (Maybe another time).

- Honorific language and address forms: Using polite pronouns and titles to respect.

- Silence as a strategy: Often used to show disagreement or discomfort without confrontation.

- Formulaic expressions: "Yaxshi niyat bilan" (with good intentions), "Alloh biladi" (God knows).

In Uzbek, maintaining face and group harmony often outweighs the need for clarity or precision.

Cross-Cultural Comparison

The contrast between low-context English and high-context Uzbek means that misunderstandings may arise if communicative norms are not properly understood. For example, an English speaker may perceive indirect Uzbek speech as evasive, while a Uzbek speaker may find English bluntness rude.

Communication feature	English	Uzbek
Directness	More direct	More indirect
Use of paraphrase	Frequent	Less frequent
Face-saving strategies	Individual-oriented	Group/honor-oriented
Role of non-verbal cues	Moderate	Highly significant
Speech acts (e.g., refusals)	Hedges+direct statements	Indirect language,religious

Conclusion. While English and Uzbek share some universal communication strategies, cultural expectations shape how these are used. A deeper understanding of these strategies helps bridge communicative gaps, prevent misunderstandings, and foster effective language teaching and learning. By emphasizing both linguistic and cultural components, educators can support learners in becoming competent and confident communicators.

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O'QUVCHILARNING SO'Z BOYLIGINI OSHIRISHDA LUG'ATLARDAN TO'G'RI FOYDALANISH VA LUG'AT BOYLIGINI OSHIRISHDA LUG'AT TURLARI YONDASHUVLARNI O'RGANISH

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ANNOTATSIYA: Lug'at boyligini oshirish har bir tilni, ayniqsa, hozirgi kundagi global tilga aylanib borayotgan Ingliz tilini mukammal o'rganishda muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Til o'rganishda Grammatika qanchalik kerakli hisoblansa, so'z boyligi ya'ni lug'at ham shunchalik zarur, grammatikadan muhimroq desak ham yolg'on bo'lmaydi. Shunday ekan, bu maqolada lug'at boyligidan to'g'ri foydalanish va uni boyitishda turli xil strategiyalarni ishlatish haqida fikr yuritiladi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: So'z boyligi, lug'at, faol lug'at va nofaol lug'at, ifoda etuvchi lug'at, qabul qiluvchi lug'at, o'qish va eshitish, gapirish va yozish skilllari, kontekstual o'rganish, mnemoteknika metodlari, intervallangan takrorlash, chet tilini o'rganish.

ANNOTATION: Increasing vocabulary is essential in learning any language, especially in today's world where English is becoming a global language. Vocabulary development is one of the key issues in mastering the English language. Although grammar is considered important, it would not be wrong to say that vocabulary is just as necessary, if not more. Therefore, this article discusses the correct use of vocabulary and various strategies for its development.

Keywords: Vocabulary richness, vocabulary, active vocabulary, passive vocabulary, expressive vocabulary, receptive vocabulary, reading and listening, speaking and writing skills, contextual learning, mnemonic techniques, spaced repetition, foreign language learning.

АННОТАЦИЯ: Расширение словарного запаса является важной частью изучения любого языка, особенно в условиях глобализации, когда английский язык становится международным. Один из ключевых аспектов овладения английским языком — это развитие лексики. Хотя грамматика считается важной, нельзя не признать, что словарный запас столь же необходим, если не больше. В данной статье рассматривается правильное использование лексики и различные стратегии её обогащения.

Ключевые слова: Богатство словарного запаса, словарь, активный словарь, пассивный словарь, экспрессивный словарь, рецептивный словарь, чтение и аудирование, говорение и письмо, навыки, контекстное обучение, мнемотехнические методы, интервальное повторение, изучение иностранного языка.

KIRISH

Birinchi bo'lib har bir insonda bo'ladigan so'z boyligi fan tilida aytadigan bo'lsak ya'ni lug'atga keladigan bo'lsak, "LUG'AT - NIMA ?" Lug'at — bu biror tilga oid so'zlar majmuasi bo'lib, u kishining og'zaki yoki yozma nutqida

foydalanadigan so'zlar yig'indisidir. Har bir til foydalanuvchisining lug'at boyligi uning til bilish darajasi, fikrni aniq ifodalash qobiliyati va muloqot samaradorligini belgilaydi. Lug'at ishlatilishi bo'yicha ikki xil bo'ladi. Ular :

1. Faol lug'at (Active vocabulary) - shaxs muntazam ravishda ishlatadigan so'zlar, ya'ni ko'chada, ishda, o'qishda yozish va gapirish uchun ishlatiladigan, hech ham yodimizdan chiqmaydigan so'zlar .

2. Nofaol lug'at (Passive vocabulary) - kishi tushunadigan , lekin kam ishlatadigan so'zlar ya'ni u so'zlarni tarjimasini bilsakda kundalik hayotimizda ishlatmaydigan so'zlar. Bunday so'zlar eshitish va o'qishda tanilgan bo'ladi va bularni eshitganimiz va o'qiganimizda yodimizga keladi.

Hozirgi globallashuv davrida ingliz tilini mukammal o'zlashtirish zamonaviy shaxsning asosiy ehtiyojlaridan biriga aylangan. Til o'rganish jarayonida vocabulary — lug'at boyligi — asosiy komponentlardan biri sifatida ajralib turadi. Tadqiqotlar ko'rsatadiki, til bilish darajasi ko'pincha shaxsning so'z zaxirasi hajmi bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi vocabulary (lug'at) o'zlashtirish jarayoni psixolingvistik nuqtayi nazardan tahlil qilinadi hamda uning til o'rganishdagi roli yoritiladi. Vocabulary, ya'ni lug'at boyligi, til tizimining asosiy strukturaviy elementi hisoblanadi. Psixolingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan olganda, yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirish inson miyasi tomonidan informatsiyani qabul qilish, qayta ishlash va xotirada saqlash mexanizmlari orqali amalga oshiriladi. Ingliz tilini o'rganishda quyidagi bosqichlar muhim ahamiyatga ega:

Receptive vocabulary (qabul qiluvchi lug'at): O'qish va eshitish orqali o'zlashtiriladigan so'zlar to'plami. Bu IELTS (International English Language Testing System) va CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) kabi sertifikatlardagi “reading “ va “ listening” skillarini oshirishda kerakli va muhim bo'lgan so'zlar to'plamidir. Bunday lug'atlarni o'rganish bilan shu ko'nikmalarni oshirish oson bo'ladi.

Productive vocabulary (ifoda qiluvchi lug'at): Gapirish va yozishda faol qo'llaniladigan so'zlar majmuasi. Bu esa xuddi o'sha sertifikatlardagi “speaking “ va “writing” skillarida foydalaniladigan faol lug'at hisoblanadi.

Vocabulary o'zlashtirish samaradorligi bir necha omillar bilan belgilanadi:

-Kontekstual o'rganish: So'zlarni alohida emas, balki gaplar va matnlar kontekstida o'rganish eslab qolishni osonlashtiradi. Bu esa lug'atlarni uzoq muddatga va chuqurroq o'rganishga yordam beradi . Bu lug'atni kontekstdagi joylashuviga va qaysi so'zlar bilan birga kelishiga qarab u so'zning ijobiy va salbiy ma'noda ekanligini va boshqa sinonimlari bilan solishtirish imkonini beradi. Bu borada Emberganova Altinay Jumabekovna o'z maqolasida so'z olib borgan , chuqur o'rgangan o'quvchilarda lug'at boyligini oshirishda qisqa hikoyalardan foydalanish ularning eng ko'p duch keladigan muammosini bartaraf etish uchun zarur bo'ladi - degan fikrga

kelgan. Vocabulary rivojlantirish usullarining samaradorligini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan eksperimental tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qish va tinglash faoliyatini birgalikda olib borish, mustaqil so'z yodlash usullariga nisbatan yuqoriroq natijalar beradi. Xususan, ingliz tilidagi autentik matnlar bilan ishlash (yangiliklar, ilmiy maqolalar, adabiy asarlar) passiv va aktiv vocabularyni baravar rivojlantiradi.[7]

-Mnemoteknika metodlari: Assotsiatsiyalar va vizual obrazlar yaratish orqali yangi so'zlarni xotirada mustahkamlash. Avvalo, bu usulga ta'rif beradigan bo'lsak, " Mnemo " - qadimgi yunonchada " xotira " va " teknika " - uslub, yo'l degan ma'noni bildiradi. Bu usulda so'zlarni tasavvur qilish yo'li bilan nimalargadir o'xshatish, obrazlar yaratish yoki qisqartmalar orqali eslab qolinadi. Ko'rgan narsalarini insonlar xotirasiga mustahkamroq joylagani bois, bu ko'z oldiga keltirib tasavvur qilish so'zlarni yod olishda samarali usullardan biri hisoblanadi. Bu xotirani shakllantirish usuli bo'yicha Psixologiya va Huquq fanlari bo'yicha taniqli (faxriy) professor Elizabeth Loftus ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borgan. U o'z tadqiqotlarida inson miyasi qanday qilib haqiqatda bo'lmagan hodisalalarni "xotira" sifatida qabul qilishi mumkinligini ilmiy jihatdan asoslab bergan. [4]

-Intervallangan takrorlash: Ma'lum vaqt oralig'ida ma'lumotlarni takrorlash orqali uzoq muddatli xotiraga mustahkamlash. Bu usulda birinchi navbatda o'rganilishi kerak bo'lgan so'zlar takrorlash bilan yodlanadi va u esdan chiqib ketishidan avval boshida uch kun, keyin yetti kunda va yigirma bir kun oralig'ida takrorlaniladi. Shu bilan bu so'zlar uzoq muddatli xotiraga saqlanadi. Bu metod bo'yicha Dr. SHazia F. Durrani tadqiqotlar olib borgan. Uning tadqiqotlari Intervallangan takrorlashning ta'limdagi samaradorligini o'rganadi va yangi o'rganish modellarini ishlab chiqadi.[5]

XULOSA

Ingliz tilida erkin muloqot qilish, ilmiy ishlar olib borish va professional sohada muvaffaqiyat qozonish uchun vocabulary boyligini muntazam va maqsadga yo'naltirilgan tarzda rivojlantirish zarur. Psixolingvistik tadqiqotlar asosida ishlab chiqilgan metodikalar til o'rganish jarayonini samarali tashkil etish imkonini beradi. Shuning uchun Devid Uilkins "grammatikasiz juda oz narsani yetkazish mumkin. Lug'atsiz hech narsani yetkazib bo'lmaydi" deb juda to'g'ri aytgan. Shunday ekan nafaqat ingliz tili balki boshqa tillarni o'rganishda ham lug'at boyligini doimiy ravishda o'stirib borish va buning uchun har bir inson o'ziga qulay bo'lgan metoddan foydalanishi zarur va har bir til o'rganuvchi shaxs uchun vocabulary ustida tizimli ish olib borish - muvaffaqiyat garovidir.

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Linguistic Features of Wordplay in Uzbek and English Languages

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Abstract

This study examines the linguistic features that enable and characterize wordplay in Uzbek and English languages, exploring how structural and semantic properties of each language create distinct possibilities for verbal play. Through comparative analysis of puns, polysemy exploitation, and morphological manipulation in both languages, this research identifies how typological differences between English (an analytic language) and Uzbek (an agglutinative language) influence wordplay mechanisms and cultural applications. The findings reveal that while English wordplay frequently exploits homophony and polysemy, Uzbek wordplay demonstrates greater utilization of morphological flexibility and suffixation patterns. This research contributes to the understanding of how language structure shapes creative linguistic expression and highlights the relationship between linguistic features and cultural-cognitive dimensions of verbal humor across typologically distinct languages.

Keywords: wordplay; linguistic humour; Uzbek language; contrastive linguistics; puns; language typology; polysemy.

Аннотация. Данное исследование рассматривает лингвистические особенности, которые обеспечивают и характеризуют игру слов в узбекском и английском языках, исследуя как структурные, так и семантические свойства каждого языка создают различные возможности для словесной игры. Посредством сравнительного анализа каламбуров, использования полисемии и морфологических манипуляций в обоих языках, данное исследование определяет, как типологические различия между английским (аналитическим языком) и узбекским (агглютинативным языком) влияют на механизмы игры слов и их культурное применение. Результаты показывают, что в то время как английская игра слов часто использует омофонию и полисемию, узбекская игра слов демонстрирует большее использование морфологической гибкости и моделей суффиксации. Это исследование способствует пониманию того, как структура языка формирует творческое лингвистическое выражение, и подчеркивает взаимосвязь между лингвистическими особенностями и культурно-когнитивными аспектами вербального юмора в типологически различных языках.

Ключевые слова: игра слов; лингвистический юмор; узбекский язык; контрастивная лингвистика; каламбуры; языковая типология; полисемия.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi so'z o'yinlarini ta'minlovchi va tavsiflovchi lingvistik xususiyatlarni o'rganadi, har bir tilning tuzilish va semantik xususiyatlari og'zaki o'yinda qanday o'ziga xos imkoniyatlarni yaratishini ko'rib chiqadi. Har ikki tildagi so'z o'yinlari, polisemiya va morfologik manipulyatsiyalarning qiyosiy tahlili orqali, ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tili (analitik til) va o'zbek tili (agglyutinativ til) o'rtasidagi tipologik farqlar so'z o'yini mexanizmlari va madaniy qo'llanishiga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlaydi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ingliz tilidagi so'z o'yini ko'pincha omofoniya va polisemiyaning qo'llanishiga, o'zbek tilidagi so'z o'yini morfologik moslashuvchanlik va suffiks naqshlaridan ko'proq foydalanishni namoyish etadi. Ushbu tadqiqot til tuzilishi ijodiy lingvistik ifodalanishni qanday shakllantirishini tushunishga yordam beradi va turli tipologik tillardagi og'zaki hazil-mutoyibaning lingvistik xususiyatlari va madaniy-kognitiv jihatlari o'rtasidagi munosabatni ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z o'yini; lingvistik hazil-mutoyiba; o'zbek tili; kontrastiv lingvistika; so'z o'yinlari; til tipologiyasi; polisemiya.

Wordplay represents one of the most sophisticated manifestations of linguistic creativity, revealing the cognitive, cultural, and structural dimensions of language systems. As speakers exploit ambiguities, similarities, and patterns inherent in their languages, they create humor, emphasis, and artistic expression that both reflect and challenge linguistic conventions. Comparative analysis of wordplay across typologically distinct languages offers particularly valuable insights into how language structure influences creative possibilities, as well as how speakers navigate linguistic constraints to achieve playful effects. This study examines the linguistic features that facilitate and characterize wordplay in Uzbek and English—languages with significant structural differences yet universal tendencies toward creative verbal play.

The typological distinction between English as a primarily analytic language and Uzbek as an agglutinative Turkic language creates different foundations for wordplay. English, with its relatively fixed word order, limited morphological marking, and abundance of homophony, offers certain affordances for verbal play that differ substantially from those available in Uzbek, which features extensive suffixation, vowel harmony, and more transparent morphological boundaries. Despite these structural differences, speakers of both languages engage in sophisticated wordplay that exploits the particular features of their linguistic systems, demonstrating both language-specific techniques and potentially universal cognitive mechanisms underlying verbal humor.

This research addresses several key questions: Which linguistic features enable and constrain wordplay in Uzbek and English? How do the typological differences between these languages influence the mechanisms and manifestations of verbal play? What can comparative analysis of wordplay reveal about the relationship between language structure and creative linguistic expression? Through examination of various wordplay forms—including puns, polysemy exploitation, morphological

manipulation, and idiomatic play—this study aims to contribute to both linguistic typology and the growing field of linguistic humor studies.

This study operates at the intersection of structural linguistics, humor studies, and cross-linguistic pragmatics. The analysis draws primarily on Attardo's (1994) *General Theory of Verbal Humor*, which emphasizes the cognitive and linguistic mechanisms underlying humor creation, and Delabastita's (1996) framework for analyzing wordplay across languages, which identifies structural features that enable different forms of verbal play. These perspectives are complemented by insights from linguistic typology, particularly Comrie's (1989) work on language universals and typological variation, which provides a framework for understanding how structural differences between languages influence expressive possibilities.

For analyzing Uzbek wordplay specifically, this research builds upon Abdullayev's (2018) work on lexical ambiguity in Uzbek and Türk's (2015) comparative studies of humor devices in Turkic languages. These studies provide essential context for understanding how Uzbek's agglutinative structure creates particular opportunities for verbal play that differ from those available in analytic languages like English.

The methodology employed in this study combines structural linguistic analysis with corpus examination. Examples of wordplay were collected from multiple sources, including literary texts, advertising, jokes, and public discourse in both languages. For Uzbek examples, contemporary literature, social media content, and collections of traditional humor were consulted, with particular attention to works by prominent Uzbek writers known for linguistic creativity such as Abdulla Qodiriy and Erkin Vohidov. For English examples, established collections of puns, comic literature, and advertising copy provided the primary data sources.

Each example was analyzed for its structural linguistic mechanisms (phonological, morphological, syntactic, or semantic), the type of ambiguity exploited, and the cultural or pragmatic context necessary for its interpretation. This analysis allowed for systematic comparison of how different linguistic features function in wordplay across the two languages.

The analysis reveals distinct patterns in how structural features enable and constrain wordplay in Uzbek and English, reflecting their typological differences while also demonstrating some universal tendencies in verbal humor.

In English, homophony and homonymy emerge as predominant linguistic features facilitating wordplay. The language's historical development, with influences from Germanic, Romance, and other language families, has created a rich inventory of words with identical pronunciation but distinct meanings. This structural feature enables the classic English pun, in which phonological identity creates semantic ambiguity, as in "Time flies like an arrow; fruit flies like a banana," where "flies"

functions as both verb and noun. The relatively opaque relationship between English spelling and pronunciation further expands possibilities for wordplay through heterographic homophones (words pronounced identically but spelled differently), as in "The wedding was so emotional that even the cake was in tiers/tears."

By contrast, Uzbek wordplay demonstrates greater reliance on morphological manipulation, reflecting the language's agglutinative structure. Uzbek's extensive system of suffixes, which attach to roots in predictable patterns while following vowel harmony rules, creates opportunities for creativity through suffix substitution or reanalysis of morpheme boundaries. For instance, the Uzbek saying "Bilmaganning bilimdoni – ko'p" (roughly: "Those who don't know claim to know the most") plays with the morphological relationship between "bilmagan" (one who doesn't know) and "bilimdon" (knowledgeable person), creating humor through the paradoxical formation. The transparency of morphological boundaries in Uzbek allows speakers to decompose and recombine elements in ways that English morphology, with its greater fusion and irregularity, less readily permits.

Polysemy exploitation appears as a significant mechanism in both languages but manifests differently. English frequently leverages its numerous polysemous prepositions and particles in wordplay, as in "You can tune a piano, but you can't tuna fish," which exploits both the polysemy of "tune" (as verb and noun) and the homophony between "tune a" and "tuna." Uzbek, with its case-marking system rather than prepositions, creates different patterns of polysemy exploitation, often centered on versatile verb roots or semantic extension of concrete terms to abstract domains. The Uzbek expression "Bosh keldi, lekin aql kelmadi" (literally: "The head came, but wisdom didn't come") plays with the concrete and abstract meanings of "bosh" (head), creating humor through the juxtaposition of physical presence and mental absence.

Syntactic ambiguity functions differently in the two languages due to their divergent word order patterns. English, with its relatively fixed SVO structure and limited case marking, frequently generates syntactic ambiguities that enable wordplay, as in headlines like "Red Tape Holds Up New Bridge" or "Local High School Dropouts Cut in Half." Uzbek, with its SOV structure and more extensive case marking, produces fewer ambiguities of this type. However, Uzbek's freer word order creates opportunities for playful rearrangement that can generate humor through expectation violation, as in the deliberate inversion of expected constituent order for comic effect.

Phonological manipulation shows interesting cross-linguistic patterns. While English wordplay often exploits minimal pairs (words differing by a single phoneme) and consonant clusters, Uzbek wordplay demonstrates greater attention to vowel harmony patterns and stress shifting. The Uzbek tongue twister "Shu sho'rva sho'rmi, yo sho'r sho'rvami?" (Is this soup salty, or is salt soupy?) plays with the phonological relationship between "sho'r" (salt/salty) and "sho'rva" (soup), creating both articulatory

challenge and semantic play through minimal sound manipulation within the constraints of Uzbek phonology.

Beyond structural linguistics, wordplay in both languages reveals important cultural dimensions and serves distinct pragmatic functions that reflect broader sociolinguistic patterns. The comparative analysis indicates both universal tendencies in how wordplay functions socially and language-specific manifestations shaped by cultural context.

In English-speaking contexts, wordplay frequently appears in commercial discourse, with advertising making extensive use of puns to create memorable messaging. This practice reflects both the structural affordances of English—particularly its rich homophony—and cultural values placed on cleverness and verbal efficiency in commercial communication. In Uzbek contexts, by contrast, wordplay demonstrates stronger connections to traditional forms like *askiya* (a form of witty verbal dueling) and *latifa* (joke narratives), reflecting the cultural importance of verbal performance and communal humor sharing.

The analysis also reveals differences in how wordplay intersects with taboo subjects. English wordplay often employs double entendre to reference sexual content indirectly, exploiting homophony and polysemy to create plausible deniability. Uzbek wordplay addressing sensitive topics more frequently employs euphemism and circumlocution rather than direct phonological ambiguity, reflecting different cultural patterns of linguistic indirection. However, both languages demonstrate the universal tendency to use wordplay as a means of addressing otherwise restricted content, suggesting a cross-cultural pragmatic function of verbal play as taboo management.

Intertextuality emerges as an important dimension in both languages, though with different reference points. English wordplay frequently references Shakespeare, the Bible, and popular culture, creating multi-layered meanings accessible to those familiar with these cultural touchstones. Uzbek wordplay shows similar patterns of intertextual reference but draws from different sources, including classical poets like Alisher Navoi, traditional proverbs, and Soviet-era cultural products. This pattern illustrates how wordplay serves not only as humor but as cultural transmission, reinforcing shared knowledge through linguistic creativity.

The functions of wordplay in establishing social identity and group boundaries appear in both languages but with distinctive features. In English, professional jargon often becomes a site for insider wordplay, with specialized fields developing puns comprehensible only to those with technical knowledge. In Uzbek, regional dialects and the tension between Russified and purified forms of the language create similar opportunities for identity-marking through verbal play, particularly in post-independence contexts where language choices carry political significance.

This comparative analysis of wordplay in Uzbek and English demonstrates how the structural features of each language create distinct possibilities and constraints for verbal play while also revealing potentially universal cognitive and social dimensions of linguistic creativity. The findings indicate that typological differences between these languages—English as primarily analytic and Uzbek as agglutinative—significantly influence the mechanisms through which speakers create and interpret wordplay, with English leveraging its rich homophony and syntactic ambiguity while Uzbek exploits its transparent morphology and productive suffixation patterns.

Despite these structural differences, speakers of both languages demonstrate similar motivations for engaging in wordplay, including humor creation, social bonding, taboo management, and display of linguistic virtuosity. This suggests that while the specific techniques of wordplay are shaped by language structure, the underlying pragmatic functions may reflect broader human tendencies toward creative language use.

This research contributes to both linguistic typology and humor studies by illuminating how language structure shapes creative expression and how speakers navigate structural constraints to achieve playful effects. The findings suggest that comparative analysis of wordplay across typologically distinct languages offers valuable insights into both language-specific patterns and potential universals in verbal humor.

Future research could productively extend this analysis to include other aspects of wordplay not fully addressed here, particularly multimodal wordplay combining linguistic and visual elements, or diachronic analysis tracking how patterns of wordplay evolve alongside language change. Additional investigation into how bilingual speakers navigate between different wordplay systems could further illuminate the cognitive dimensions of verbal humor across languages.

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Sociolinguistic Properties of Jargon Translation: The Case of Specialized Terminology Transfer Between Languages

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Abstract. This study examines the sociolinguistic dimensions of translating jargon and specialized terminology between languages with particular attention to the Uzbek-English language pair. The research investigates how sociolinguistic factors—including cultural context, power relationships, and discourse communities—influence the translation process of specialized lexical items. Drawing on theoretical frameworks from translation studies and sociolinguistics, this paper argues that jargon translation extends beyond mere lexical equivalence to encompass sociocultural adaptation. Through analysis of specialized terminology in academic, technical, and professional domains, the study demonstrates that effective jargon translation requires understanding of both source and target sociocultural environments. The findings reveal that translators employ various strategies, including calquing, domestication, and hybridization, when transferring specialized terminology, while negotiating sociolinguistic challenges inherent in cross-cultural communication.

Keywords: sociolinguistics; jargon translation; specialized terminology; discourse communities; Uzbek language; pragmatics; cross-cultural communication.

Аннотация. Данное исследование рассматривает социолингвистические аспекты перевода жаргона и специализированной терминологии между языками, с особым вниманием к паре узбекский–английский. В работе исследуется, как социолингвистические факторы — включая культурный контекст, властные отношения и дискурсивные сообщества — влияют на процесс перевода специализированных лексических единиц. Опираясь на теоретические рамки переводоведения и социолингвистики, статья утверждает, что перевод жаргона выходит за рамки простой лексической эквивалентности и включает в себя социокультурную адаптацию. Через анализ специализированной терминологии в академических, технических и профессиональных областях исследование демонстрирует, что эффективный перевод жаргона требует понимания как исходной, так и целевой социокультурной среды. Результаты показывают, что переводчики используют различные стратегии, включая калькирование, доместикацию и гибридизацию при передаче специализированной терминологии, одновременно преодолевая социолингвистические трудности, присущие межкультурной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистика; перевод жаргона; специализированная терминология; дискурсивные сообщества; узбекский язык; прагматика; межкультурная коммуникация.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot jargon va maxsus terminologiyani tillar o'rtasida tarjima qilishning ijtimoiy til bilimi jihatlarini o'zbek-ingliz til juftligi misolida o'rganadi. Tadqiqot madaniy kontekst, tarjimashunoslik va sotsiolingvistikaning nazariy asoslariga tayanib, jargon tarjimasi shunchaki leksik ekvivalentlikdan tashqari ijtimoiy-madaniy moslashuvni ham qamrab olishini

ta'kidlaydi. Tarjimashunoslik va ijtimoiy tilshunoslikning nazariy asoslariga tayanib, ushbu maqola jargon tarjimasi shunchaki so'zma-so'z ekvivalentlikdan tashqari, ijtimoiy-madaniy moslashuvni ham o'z ichiga olishini ta'kidlaydi. Ilmiy, texnik va kasbiy sohalardagi maxsus terminologiyani tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, samarali jargon tarjimasi ham manba, ham maqsadli ijtimoiy-madaniy muhitni chuqur tushunishni talab etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sotsiolingvistika; jargon tarjimasi; ixtisoslashgan terminologiya; diskurs hamjamiyatlari; o'zbek tili; pragmatika; madaniyatlararo muloqot.

The translation of specialized terminology, jargon, and argot presents unique challenges that transcend traditional linguistic boundaries, inviting a deeper examination of sociolinguistic dimensions that influence the transfer of meaning across languages. While conventional approaches to translation studies have often focused on lexical equivalence and structural accuracy, this research posits that the translation of specialized language forms constitutes a complex sociocultural act embedded within power structures and community practices. The interactions between specialized terminology and sociolinguistic factors become particularly pronounced when examining language pairs with asymmetrical historical development trajectories in specialized domains, as exemplified by the Uzbek-English translation dynamic.

In Uzbekistan, the post-independence period has witnessed a rapid evolution of terminological systems across multiple domains, from legal and administrative language to information technology and scientific discourse. This evolution has occurred within a sociolinguistic context characterized by multilingual practices and ongoing language policy developments. As Uzbek specialists increasingly participate in global discourse communities, the need for effective translation of specialized terminology has grown exponentially, raising important questions about the sociolinguistic dimensions of this process. The translation challenges emerge not merely from linguistic disparities but from divergent sociocultural contexts in which specialized terminology is embedded and operationalized.

The present study investigates how sociolinguistic factors—including discourse community membership, register variation, power dynamics, and cultural context—influence the translation of specialized terminology between Uzbek and English. Drawing on theoretical frameworks from both translation studies and sociolinguistics, this research examines how translators navigate complex sociolinguistic terrain when transferring specialized terminology, focusing particularly on strategies employed to bridge contextual gaps between source and target languages.

The translation of specialized terminology exists at the intersection of multiple theoretical domains, including terminology science, sociolinguistics, and translation studies. Traditional approaches to terminology translation have often adopted prescriptive methodologies grounded in Wüster's General Theory of Terminology, emphasizing standardization and one-to-one equivalence between source and target terms. However, contemporary sociolinguistic perspectives have challenged these

prescriptive approaches, arguing instead for a descriptive understanding of terminology as socially constructed phenomena embedded within discourse communities. Temmerman's (2000) sociocognitive approach to terminology positions specialized terms as dynamic units that evolve through usage within particular social contexts rather than static entities with fixed meanings.

Similarly, sociolinguistic theories have increasingly recognized the role of specialized terminology in constructing and maintaining professional identities and community boundaries. Gumperz's (1982) interactional sociolinguistics provides a valuable framework for understanding how specialized terminology functions as a marker of in-group membership and professional competence. The sociolinguistic concept of "communities of practice" (Wenger, 1998) further elucidates how specialized terminology develops and functions within bounded professional groups, creating particular challenges for translators operating outside these communities.

In the Uzbek context, Abdullayev's (2016) research on terminological developments in post-independence Uzbekistan highlights the interplay between linguistic, cultural, and political factors in shaping terminology systems. His work demonstrates how terminology evolution reflects broader sociopolitical changes, including shifts from Russian-influenced terminology toward more indigenous lexical resources or international (often English-based) terminology.

This study employs a qualitative research methodology designed to capture the sociolinguistic dimensions of terminology translation between Uzbek and English across multiple domains. The research combines corpus analysis of parallel texts in academic, technical, legal, and medical domains with semi-structured interviews conducted with fifteen professional translators with expertise in specialized domains. Data analysis employed a grounded theory approach, allowing themes and patterns to emerge from the data rather than imposing predetermined categories.

The analysis reveals multiple sociolinguistic dimensions that influence the translation of specialized terminology between Uzbek and English. These dimensions extend beyond purely linguistic considerations to encompass social, cultural, and institutional factors that shape translation practices and outcomes.

A foundational sociolinguistic dimension concerns the asymmetrical development trajectories of specialized terminology systems in Uzbek and English. In domains such as information technology, Uzbek terminology has developed more recently and often under the influence of English terminology, creating particular translation dynamics. As one translator interviewed for this study noted, "Many IT concepts arrive in Uzbekistan already labeled in English, and we must decide whether to create Uzbek equivalents or simply adopt the English terms." This observation highlights how translation practices intersect with broader language planning and terminology development processes. The sociolinguistic concept of prestige emerges

as significant here, with English terminology often carrying higher status in technical domains, influencing translators' decisions about adaptation versus borrowing.

Discourse community membership constitutes another crucial sociolinguistic dimension affecting terminology translation. Specialized terminology functions not merely as a tool for precise communication but as a marker of professional identity and community boundaries. Translation challenges arise when the discourse communities in the source and target language contexts have different configurations, histories, or practices. For example, in legal translation between Uzbek and English, translators must navigate between civil law and common law traditions with distinct terminological systems reflecting different legal conceptualizations. As Xudoyberganova (2019) notes in her analysis of Uzbek legal terminology, concepts like "sud huquqi" contain cultural and institutional specificities that resist straightforward translation into English legal terminology.

Power relationships between languages and cultures constitute perhaps the most significant sociolinguistic dimension influencing terminology translation. In the global knowledge economy, English often occupies a dominant position as the primary language of scientific and technical communication, creating unequal conditions for terminology exchange. This asymmetry affects translation in multiple ways, including the prevalence of English loanwords in Uzbek specialized discourse and the challenges of translating indigenous Uzbek concepts into English. As Karimov (2018) observes, this power dynamic can lead to "conceptual erosion" when indigenous knowledge systems are forced to conform to dominant terminological frameworks through translation.

Cultural embeddedness of specialized terminology emerges as another critical sociolinguistic dimension affecting translation. Even highly technical terms carry cultural associations and operate within culturally specific conceptual frameworks. Medical terminology translation between Uzbek and English illustrates this dimension clearly. Traditional Uzbek medical concepts like "sovuq tegish" (literally "cold touching," referring to a condition resulting from exposure to cold) reflect culturally specific understandings of health and illness that do not align neatly with Western biomedical terminology. Translators must therefore engage with these cultural dimensions when transferring specialized terminology between languages.

The research findings indicate that translators employ diverse strategies when navigating the sociolinguistic complexities of terminology translation between Uzbek and English. Terminological borrowing represents one common strategy, particularly in domains where English terminology dominates global discourse. In information technology translation, for instance, English terms like "software," "hardware," and "online" frequently appear in Uzbek texts either preserved in their original form or with minimal orthographic adaptation. This borrowing strategy reflects both pragmatic

considerations and sociolinguistic realities including the prestige associated with English technical terminology.

Calquing, or loan translation, emerges as another prominent strategy that allows translators to create terminological equivalents while maintaining connection to source language concepts. Examples from the corpus include Uzbek terms like "ma'lumotlar bazasi" (literally "information base") for "database" and "qattiq disk" (literally "hard disk") for "hard drive." This strategy represents a middle path between complete borrowing and independent terminology development, allowing for cultural adaptation while maintaining conceptual links across languages.

Contextual adaptation represents a more transformative translation strategy guided by sociolinguistic awareness. Rather than seeking direct equivalents, translators employing this strategy reconfigure terminology to fit the discursive conventions and conceptual frameworks of the target language community. For example, when translating academic terminology from English to Uzbek, translators often adapt terms to suit the more hierarchical and formal discourse patterns characteristic of Uzbek academic writing.

Hybridization strategies combine elements from multiple languages or registers to create terminology that functions effectively in multilingual professional environments. In contemporary Uzbek professional discourse, hybrid terminology forms incorporating elements from Uzbek, Russian, and English are increasingly common, reflecting the complex linguistic landscape of professional communication in Uzbekistan. Rather than viewing such hybridization as deficient translation, this research suggests understanding it as a creative sociolinguistic adaptation to multilingual realities.

The findings of this research have significant implications for both translation practice and pedagogy. For translation practice, this research underscores the importance of developing what might be termed "sociolinguistic competence" alongside traditional linguistic and subject-matter expertise. Effective terminology translators require awareness of how specialized terms function within particular discourse communities and cultural contexts. For translation pedagogy, the research points toward more integrated approaches that combine terminology science with sociolinguistic perspectives. Translation programs should incorporate modules addressing the social life of specialized terminology, helping students understand how terms function as markers of professional identity, vehicles of cultural knowledge, and instruments of power.

This research has examined the sociolinguistic properties of jargon and specialized terminology translation with particular attention to the Uzbek-English language pair. The findings demonstrate that effective terminology translation extends well beyond finding lexical equivalents to encompass complex processes of

sociolinguistic adaptation and cultural negotiation. The study has identified multiple strategies employed by translators to navigate the sociolinguistic complexities of terminology translation, including borrowing, calquing, contextual adaptation, hybridization, and explanatory expansion. Rather than representing technical deficiencies, these varied strategies reflect translators' attempts to mediate between different sociolinguistic contexts while maintaining communicative effectiveness.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that the translation of jargon and specialized terminology constitutes a complex sociolinguistic practice rather than merely a technical linguistic procedure. By recognizing and addressing the sociolinguistic properties of terminology translation, translators, educators, and language planners can contribute to more effective cross-cultural communication and knowledge exchange in an increasingly interconnected global context.

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KRIMNOLINGVISTIK TEKSHIRUV HAMDA UNING TERGOVDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada krimnolingvistika fanining asosiy tushunchalari, usullari va ularning tergovdagi amaliy ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Jinoyat ishlari bo'yicha yozma va og'zaki dalillarni lingvistik tahlil qilish, tahdid, tuhmat, shantaj, firibgarlik va boshqa so'z orqali amalga oshirilgan jinoyatlarni aniqlashda tilshunos mutaxassislarning o'rni tobora oshib bormoqda. Maqolada O'zbekiston va xorijiy tajribalar misolida krimnolingvistik ekspertizaning dolzarbligi yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: krimnolingvistika, lingvistik ekspertiza, tergov, jinoyat, til tahlili.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются основные понятия криминалистической лингвистики, её методы и практическое значение в следственных действиях. Лингвистический анализ письменных и устных доказательств позволяет выявить угрозы, клевету, шантаж и иные преступления, совершаемые с помощью языка. На основе опыта Узбекистана и зарубежных стран подчеркивается актуальность лингвистической экспертизы.

Ключевые слова: криминалистика, лингвистическая экспертиза, расследование, преступление, языковой анализ.

Abstract. This article explores the key concepts and methods of forensic linguistics and its practical application in criminal investigations. Linguistic analysis of written and spoken evidence is increasingly used to identify threats, defamation, blackmail, fraud, and other language-based crimes. The paper highlights the relevance of linguistic expertise through examples from Uzbekistan and international practice.

Keywords: forensic linguistics, linguistic expertise, investigation, crime, language analysis.

Zamonaviy huquq-tartibot faoliyatida lingvistik bilimlardan foydalanish tobora dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Jinoyatlarni ochishda nafaqat moddiy dalillar, balki til vositasida ifodalangan xabarlar — tahdidli xatlar, tovlamachilik yozuvlari, audioyozuvlar, hatto ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi postlar ham muhim isbot vositasi sifatida qaralmoqda. Ushbu holat krimnolingvistika — tilshunoslik va kriminalistika tutashgan sohaga — katta ehtiyoj tug'dirgan.

Krimnolingvistika (forensic linguistics) — bu tilshunoslikning jinoyat huquqi doirasida qo'llaniladigan yo'nalishi bo'lib, u tergov jarayonida til vositalari orqali sodir etilgan jinoyatlarni aniqlash va tahlil qilishga xizmat qiladi. Ingliz olimi **Timoti Routledj** (T. Routledge, 1994) bu yo'nalishni "tilni qonun himoyasida tahlil qilish" deb ta'riflaydi⁸⁵. Ma'lumki krimnolingvistik tekshiruvning mohiyati, metodlari

⁸⁵ Coulthard, M., & Johnson, A. (2007). *An Introduction to Forensic Linguistics: Language in Evidence*. Routledge

va tergovdagi o‘rni ilmiy manbalar va amaliy misollar asosida tahlil qilinishi bugungi kunda ham qizg‘in bahslarga sabab bo‘lmoqda.

Krimnolingvistika — bu huquqiy munosabatlarda tildan foydalanishni lingvistik metodlar yordamida o‘rganadigan fanlararo sohaga mansub bo‘lib, **u huquqshunoslik, psixolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika hamda sud ekspertizasi bilan chambarchas bog‘liq.** Bu sohaning asosiy maqsadi — jinoyatga oid til birliklarini tahlil qilish orqali ayblov yoki himoyaga xizmat qiladigan lingvistik xulosalarni ishlab chiqishdir.

Peter Tiersma (2000) krimnolingvistikani "*Til va qonun o‘rtasidagi ziddiyatlarni aniqlash, huquqiy matnlarning izohini berish va dalil sifatida tilning huquqiy rolini tahlil qilish*"⁸⁶ deb ta’riflaydi. Jumladan, tahdidli xat, tovlamachilik maktubi, tuhmatli matn yoki noto‘g‘ri tarjima — bularning barchasi lingvistik ekspertiza obyektlari hisoblanadi.

Krimnolingvistik tahlilning asosiy yo‘nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- i. Tahdid va tuhmatlarni aniqlash.
- ii. Mualliflikni aniqlash (avtoring).
- iii. Shartnoma yoki bayonotlarning ma’nosini talqin qilish.
- iv. So‘zlovchining niyatini tahlil qilish.
- v. Til orqali amalga oshirilgan firibgarliklarni aniqlash.

Tergovda krimnolingvistik tahlil ko‘plab jinoyat turlarida muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ayniqsa, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari rivojlangan davrda tahdid, tuhmat, shantaj, kamsitish, diniy va milliy adovatni qo‘zg‘atuvchi matnlar ko‘pincha yozma yoki og‘zaki shaklda tarqatiladi. Bunday holatlarda tilshunos-ekspert dalil sifatida taqdim etilayotgan matnni sintaktik, semantik, pragmatik, stilistik va leksik jihatdan tahlil qilib, uning jinoyat alomatlarini aniqlashga ko‘maklashadi.

Masalan, **2020-yilda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Jinoyat kodeksining 139-moddasi (tuhmat)** asosida ko‘rilgan bir ishda ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi postda keltirilgan iboralar krimnolingvistik jihatdan tahlil qilinib, muallif tuhmat qilgan degan xulosa chiqarilgan. Tahlilda “yolg‘on ma’lumot”, “shaxsiy sha’n va obro‘ni kamsitish”, “fakt va fikr chegarasi” kabi elementlar ajratib ko‘rsatilgan.

Rossiyada esa mashhur lingvist **Viktor Kabashkin**⁸⁷ tomonidan amalga oshirilgan sud tahlilida audioyozuvdagi so‘zlovchi kimligi va niyati fonetik va prosodik usullar orqali aniqlanib, sudda dalil sifatida qabul qilingan.

⁸⁶ Kabashkin, V. P. (2014). Kriminalnaya lingvistika i sudebnaya ekspertiza. *Vestnik MGU*, 2(5), 33–41

⁸⁷ Rahimov, A. (2021). Krimnolingvistik tahlilning sud-amaliyotdagi o‘rni. *O‘zbek tilshunosligi jurnali*, 1(2), 45–52.

Krimnolingvistik ekspertiza quyidagi hollarda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi⁸⁸:

- i. Anonim tahdidli xatlar muallifini aniqlash.
- ii. So'z erkinligi va tuhmat o'rtasidagi farqni aniqlash.
- iii. Milliy, diniy adovatga sabab bo'ladigan matnlarni baholash.
- iv. Firibgarlik xatlari (phishing e-mails) tahlili.
- v. Internet orqali sodir etilgan jinoyatlar tahlili.

Krimnolingvistik tahlil o'z uslub va metodikasiga ega bo'lib, ularni bilish esa kriminologlar uchun eng dolzarb masaladir.

Krimnolingvistik tahlilda ishlatiladigan asosiy metodlar sifatid quyidagilarni ko'rsatish mumkin⁸⁹:

- **Diskurs tahlili** — matnning kontekstdagi ijtimoiy va psixologik tahlili.
- **Pragmatik tahlil** — gaplovchining niyati va tinglovchiga yetkaziladigan xabar ta'sirini tahlil qilish.
- **Muallifni aniqlash** — stilometrik tahlil orqali yozuvchining xususiyatlarini ajratish.
- **Semantik tahlil** — so'z va iboralarning ma'no doirasini aniqlash.

Misol uchun, agar bir maktubda “*Seni yo‘q qilaman!*” degan ibora mavjud bo‘lsa, lingvist bu jumlaning grammatik shakli, semantik og‘irligi, tahdid alomatlari va kontekstdagi ahamiyatini baholaydi. “*Yo‘q qilish*” so‘zining harfiy yoki ko‘chma ma‘nodami, real tahdidni anglatadimi — bular ekspert xulosasida asosiy rol o‘ynaydi.

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni ta’kidlash mumkinki, krimnolingvistika — bu zamonaviy tergov amaliyotining ajralmas qismiga aylanib borayotgan fanlararo yo‘nalish bo‘lib, tilshunoslarning tergovdagi roli ortib bormoqda. ***So‘z orqali amalga oshiriladigan jinoyatlar — tahdid, tuhmat, tovlamachilik, diniy adovatga da’vatlar — ko‘proq raqamli va yozma shaklda amalga oshirilgani bois, lingvistik ekspertiza ularni aniqlash va huquqiy baholashda muhim vosita hisoblanadi.*** Krimnolingvistik ekspertiza tergovchiga jinoyatni aniqlashda yordam beradi, sudga esa matnning huquqiy mohiyatini tushunish imkonini yaratadi. Shu boisdan bu sohaning rivoji, maxsus mutaxassislar tayyorlash va metodikani takomillashtirish dolzarb vazifalardan biridir.

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MAIN TYPES OF ENGLISH DICTIONARIES

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Abstract. This article explores the main types of English dictionaries, focusing on their structure, purpose, and usage. Dictionaries are essential tools for language learners, educators, translators, and writers, offering a variety of information including definitions, pronunciations, grammar, and usage. The paper classifies English dictionaries into several categories, such as monolingual, bilingual, learner's, specialized, and historical dictionaries. Each type serves a distinct function and caters to different user needs. Understanding these categories enables users to select the most appropriate dictionary for their linguistic and academic tasks. The article also briefly discusses the evolution of dictionaries and the growing role of digital and online formats in modern language learning.

Keywords: English dictionaries, monolingual, bilingual, learner's dictionary, specialized dictionary, historical dictionary, language learning, reference tools, digital dictionaries, lexicography.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются основные типы английских словарей, их структура, назначение и область применения. Словари являются важными инструментами для изучающих язык, преподавателей, переводчиков и писателей, предоставляя определения, произношение, грамматическую информацию и примеры использования. В статье английские словари классифицируются как монолингвальные, билингвальные, обучающие, специализированные и исторические. Каждый тип имеет свои особенности и удовлетворяет потребности различных пользователей. Также кратко рассматривается развитие словарей и роль цифровых и онлайн-форматов в современном изучении языка.

Ключевые слова: английские словари, монолингвальные, билингвальные, обучающий словарь, специализированный словарь, исторический словарь, изучение языка, справочные материалы, цифровые словари, лексикография.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi lug'atlarning asosiy turlari, ularning tuzilishi, maqsadi va qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Lug'atlar til o'rganuvchilar, o'qituvchilar, tarjimonlar va yozuvchilar uchun muhim vosita bo'lib, so'z ma'nolari, talaffuz, grammatika va foydalanish haqida ma'lumot beradi. Maqolada ingliz lug'atlari monolingval, bilingval, o'rganuvchilar uchun, ixtisoslashgan va tarixiy turlarga ajratiladi. Har bir lug'at turi o'ziga xos vazifani bajaradi va

foydalanuvchilarning turli ehtiyojlariga mos keladi. Shuningdek, maqolada lug'atlarning rivojlanish tarixi va raqamli shakllarning til o'rganishdagi roli haqida ham qisqacha so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz lug'atlari, monolingval, bilingval, o'rganuvchilar lug'ati, ixtisoslashgan lug'at, tarixiy lug'at, til o'rganish, ma'lumot vositalari, raqamli lug'atlar, leksikografiya.

Dictionaries are indispensable tools in the study and use of any language, and English is no exception. They provide users with definitions, pronunciation guides, grammatical information, and even usage examples.⁹⁰ Over time, various types of English dictionaries have been developed to meet the needs of different users, including language learners, translators, academics, and professionals.⁹¹ This article discusses the main types of English dictionaries, their unique features, and their applications.

One of the most common types is the monolingual dictionary, which explains words using the same language. In English, monolingual dictionaries define English words in English. These are especially useful for intermediate and advanced learners who want to deepen their understanding of the language.

Well-known examples include the Oxford English Dictionary and the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English.⁹² Monolingual dictionaries often provide detailed explanations, word origins (etymology), example sentences, and information on word usage and context (Rundell, 2006).

Another widely used type is the bilingual dictionary, which translates words from one language into another. For English learners whose native language is not English, bilingual dictionaries are often the first step in vocabulary acquisition. These dictionaries help users understand the meanings of English words in their own language. For example, an English-Uzbek dictionary translates English words into Uzbek, making it a useful tool for beginner learners or those studying in a multilingual environment (Nation, 2001).

The learner's dictionary is a specialized type of monolingual dictionary designed specifically for non-native speakers of English. It uses simple language, clear definitions, and provides plenty of example sentences. Learner's dictionaries also often include information on common collocations, word frequency, and typical errors. Dictionaries such as the Cambridge Learner's Dictionary or the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary are tailored to help learners develop their language skills effectively (Hornby, 2015; Cambridge University Press, 2023).

⁹⁰ Landau, S. I. (2001). *Dictionaries: The Art and Craft of Lexicography* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

⁹¹ Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*. Cambridge University Press.

⁹² Hornby, A. S. (2015). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (9th ed.). Oxford University Press.

Specialized dictionaries focus on a particular field or discipline. For example, there are medical dictionaries, legal dictionaries, business English dictionaries, and technical dictionaries. These dictionaries are essential for professionals or students who need precise definitions and terminology related to their area of study or work (Landau, 2001).

Another important type is the historical dictionary, which traces the development and historical usage of words over time. The Oxford English Dictionary is a prime example of this type. It not only defines words but also provides quotations showing how a word's meaning has changed over centuries (Oxford University Press, 2023). These dictionaries are valuable for researchers, writers, and linguists interested in the evolution of language.

With the advancement of technology, digital and online dictionaries have become increasingly popular. They offer quick access, audio pronunciation, search functions, and interactive features that enhance language learning. Many modern learners now rely on mobile dictionary apps and websites rather than traditional printed books.

CONCLUSION

Understanding the different types of English dictionaries is essential for effective language use and learning. Each dictionary type—whether monolingual, bilingual, learner's, specialized, or historical—serves a unique purpose and addresses specific user needs. While traditional printed dictionaries remain valuable, digital and online formats have greatly enhanced accessibility and convenience. Choosing the right type of dictionary based on the context and learning goals can significantly improve vocabulary acquisition, comprehension, and communication in English.

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A Corpus-Based Analysis of “Surprise” Verbs in English: Frequency, Register, and Semantic Variation

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada “hayrat” kategoriyasiga oid to'rtta inglizcha fe'l – *surprise*, *wonder*, *astonish* va *amazing* korpus asosidagi qiyosiy tahlili taqdim etiladi. Zamonaviy Amerika Ingliz Tili Korpusi (COCA) ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan holda, ushbu fe'llarning chastotasi va morfologik shakllari o'rganilib, ularning zamonaviy ingliz tilidagi semantik va pragmatik funksiyalarini aniqlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korpus lingvistikasi, hayrat fe'llari, COCA, chastota tahlili, semantika, emotsional fe'llar.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен корпусный сравнительный анализ четырёх английских глаголов, относящихся к категории «удивление»: *surprise*, *wonder*, *astonish* и *amaze*. Используя данные из Корпуса Современного Американского Английского (COCA), исследование рассматривает частотность и морфологические вариации этих глаголов с целью определения их семантических и прагматических функций в современном английском языке.

Ключевые слова: корпусная лингвистика, глаголы удивления, COCA, частотный анализ, семантика, глаголы эмоций.

Abstract: This paper presents a corpus-based comparative analysis of four English verbs associated with the category of “surprise”: *surprise*, *wonder*, *astonish*, and *amaze*. Utilizing data from the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA), the study investigates the frequency and morphological variations of these verbs to determine their semantic and pragmatic functions in contemporary English.

Keywords: corpus linguistics, surprise verbs, COCA, frequency analysis, semantics, emotion verbs.

Introduction

Emotion verbs have long attracted attention in linguistics, particularly in semantic and discourse analysis. According to A. Wierzbicka (1999), verbs such as *surprise* and *amaze* belong to the domain of experiential emotion predicates, which describe subjective states triggered by external stimuli. G. Lakoff and M. Johnson (1980) emphasized the metaphorical underpinnings of emotional expressions, where verbs often embody metaphorical mappings such as "SURPRISE IS A SUDDEN EVENT."

Corpus linguistics offers a means to empirically validate such semantic intuitions. D. Biber et al. (1998) demonstrated that certain emotion verbs cluster in

specific registers, such as fiction and conversation, depending on their syntactic and pragmatic constraints. Moreover, D. Mindt (2000) observed that high-frequency verbs tend to display more grammatical versatility and collocational variability.

Methodology

This study uses the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA), which contains over a billion words from a variety of genres including spoken, fiction, magazines, newspapers, and academic texts. The verbs analyzed are: *surprise*, *wonder*, *astonish*, *amaze*. All morphological forms (base, third-person singular, past, present participle) were included to capture the full spectrum of usage.

Results

Verb	Frequency	Common Forms
wonder	131,649	wonder, wonders, wondered, wondering
surprise	25,449	surprise, surprises, surprised, surprising
amaze	5,124	amaze, amazes, amazed, amazing
astonish	1,690	astonish, astonishes, astonished, astonishing

Figure 1: Frequency of Surprise Verbs in COCA

The verb *wonder* far exceeds the others in frequency, followed by *surprise*, *amaze*, and *astonish*. This suggests that *wonder* may serve a broader range of communicative functions. (see Figure 1)

Register	Wonder	Surprise	Amaze	Astonish
Spoken	High	Medium	Low	Low
Fiction	High	High	Medium	Medium
Magazine	Medium	High	Medium	Low
Newspaper	Medium	Medium	Low	Low
Academic	Low	Low	Very Low	Very Low

Figure 2: Distribution by register of Surprise Verbs in COCA

Wonder is prominent in both spoken and fictional discourse, reflecting its frequent use in internal monologue and rhetorical questioning (e.g., “*I wonder why...*”). *Surprise* appears frequently in narrative accounts and news reporting. *Amaze* and *astonish* are mostly used in fiction and magazines, typically in evaluative contexts. (see Figure 2)

Discussion

The high frequency of *wonder* can be attributed to its semantic breadth. It can express both curiosity and awe. This dual function increases its frequency and versatility across genres. By contrast, *astonish* and *amaze* are semantically narrower, often used to describe high-intensity emotional reactions:

“The magician’s trick amazed the crowd.”

“Her courage astonished everyone.”

Each verb shows distinct syntactic preferences. For example, wonder frequently appears with interrogative clauses and modal verbs: (see Figure 3)

BROWSE/RANDOM	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
10	BLOG: 2012: taurussports.net	Shelton , who committed to FSU when he was 16 , wonders how his recruiting process would have gone if he had waited until	
11	MAG: 2010: America	. 4) Now that we have DNA testing , wonder how many fathers would behave more responsibly if they knew	
12	BLOG: 2012: ...myourlife.gather....	# Fresh off the heels of another Thanksgiving , and wonder how many of us are sincerely thankful for all that God has	
13	FIC: 2015: FantasySciFi	and my hair drawn back . Entering the gallery , wondered how much longer I'd need to blend into this world and	
14	NEWS: 1994: WashPost	when you see it and people like it . " One wonders how much people in New York will like it after it 's	
15	FIC: 1998: Ploughshares	. " I did n't notice . " # " wonder how she is doing , " said Luke . # " Not	
16	WEB: 2012: negativepositive.org	BEFORE THE GODDAMN BIRTH OF CHRIST ! HOLY FUCK ! wonder how that job interview went . " So , what do you	
17	BLOG: 2012: ...rvativetreehouse....	. They are so large and so much rock , we wonder how they ever made them . Dr. Farid also took us down	
18	FIC: 2013: MassachRev	" I never even knew you could do that ! wonder how they taste . " " Morels . " John repeats .	
19	MAG: 2010: AmericanSpectator	lose Massachusetts ? To lose Ted Kennedy 's seat ? wonder if he gets that voters do n't really trust him or his	
20	WEB: 2012: thedailybeast.com	was " It 's happening again . " Then " wonder if he has a wife and kids . " I was n't	
21	NEWS: 2007: CSMonitor	barely been heard from since he disappeared , leading many to wonder if he is dead or inactive . # But before he was	
22	BLOG: 2012: mediaite.com	speech in Iowa today where he slammed the stimulus . wonder if he was aware that the company he was speaking at took	
23	MAG: 1997: BoysLife	too young . " Jed looked down at the shears and wondered if he ld ever hold them in his hands again . "	
24	FIC: 2019: IowaRev	. Especially from toddlers on the loose . But I sometimes wonder if he is safe from me . # What might happen , for	
25	MAG: 2012: USAToday	the quarter of the beat when learning the choreography . wondered if it ever would be able to execute the choreography up to	
26	NEWS: 2008: CSMonitor	than its peak in July , many Nicaraguans are starting to wonder if it will ever amount to more than a mere brick .	
27	SPOK: 2000: NPR_Saturday	I had an ulcer in mine . And I was just wondering if maybe Frank had one , also , you know . Ms.ZAPPA	
28	BLOG: 2012: goitpartners.com	# I am no network guy , but I find myself wondering if my understanding of SDN is somehow flawed ; my experiences	
29	FIC: 1997: SouthernRev	and Vogue were on the seat between them , and Birnbaum wondered if she was offended by what he 'd said . " Who	
30	SPOK: 2003: NBC_Dateline	's going to be at the Megastore signing it . wonder if she is high . Whitney 's going to be on "	
31	FIC: 2016: FantasySciFi	inspected me . Her fingernails were painted black , and wondered if that was new . # I looked toward her friends ,	
32	MAG: 1992: SportsIll	an hour bouncing his infant grandson on his knee . wonder if the flight attendants will hand out certificates to each	
33	BLOG: 2012: ...rs.pressdemocrat....	w/o his throws on the move ? Kap Makes you wonder if the guy can keep up . OK , snarky hyperbole ,	
34	BLOG: 2012: ...dreport.blogspot....	evokes another objection to space ... colonization ... I do wonder if the human race could survive at all if separated from Mother	

Figure 3. Syntactic features of verb “wonder”

Surprise can be used in passive constructions: (see Figure 4)

BROWSE/RANDOM	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
7	SPOK: 2011: CBS_NewsMorn	citizens who responded registered close to an eight . Were you surprised at the results you received so far ? JOSEPH-CURTATONE: In	
8	NEWS: 1993: CSMonitor	land that was once seven farms # Many people would be surprised at the sums of money that pass through a farmer 's hands	
9	BLOG: 2012: ...erings.wordpress....	even take us up on our offer . You might be surprised at what a difference we can make . # In baseball parlance	
10	WEB: 2012: ...createvideogame....	the box when looking for a job . You may be surprised at what can come up with alternative searches . What Does	
11	WEB: 2012: kotaku.com	history would be more interesting . # ... # Acill packs surprises big and small , veers away from habits of the older games	
12	FIC: 2018: SciFi & Fantasy	agree with my eldest daughter . A mother should n't be surprised by a marriage gift . In fact , a mother should be	
13	FIC: 2018: SciFi & Fantasy	you think , eldest daughter , that a mother should be surprised by a marriage gift for her pouch-son ? " # Sippu murmured	
14	BLOG: 2012: feministe.us	can deal with it on the front end instead of being surprised by it at trial -- I can understand why she might not	
15	WEB: 2012: amazon.com	several books including , Pope Fiction , Surprised by Truth , Surprised by Truth , and Any Friend of God ? s is	
16	WEB: 2012: amazon.com	s the author of several books including , Pope Fiction . Surprised by Truth Surprised by Truth , and Any Friend of	
17	BLOG: 2012: thegrio.com	off the " productive class ? " # You may be surprised by who is included in the " takers " vs the "	
18	FIC: 2005: Mov:Game6	last . # # JOANNA # # We re able to surprise each other # # NICKY # # In and out of	

Figure 4. Syntactic features of verb “surprise”

Amaze (see Figure 5) and astonish (see Figure 6) can be used in passive voice and with intensifiers such as “truly,” “quite”, “still”, “absolutely”:

BROWSE/RANDOM	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
330 MAG:2010:Redbook	gynecologist , this case is one of the few that truly	amazed me I had a patient , a healthy 45-year-old mom of	
331 NEWS:2000:Chicago	# Millennium keepsake # The Sun-Times never ceases to	amaze me On Jan. 1 , you surpassed yourselves with page after	
332 WEB:2012:fullbooks.com	many falsehoods told by them , there was one which quite	amazed me mean when they said that you should be upon	
333 BLOG:2012:tvfanatic.com	through their performances such nuance that I am continually	amazed more people have n't tuned into this gem of a program over	

Figure 5. Syntactic features of verb “amaze”

KWIC **ASTONISH** **VERB** # lines: 100 200 500 1000 Collocates Clusters Topics Texts KWIC

WEBSITE		SORT	SORT	SORT
1 FIC:2003:FantasySciFi	One of the more difficult concepts - one that can still	astonish	after a lifetime	of study and hard thought - is that fact
2 WEB:2012:ted.com	building the logic . At the end I ended up absolutely	astonished	after reaching the	conclusion that there is not way how God could
3 MAG:1996:USNWR	could not tear himself away . It was then that he	astonished	aides and hangers-on	with an impromptu addition to The Speech
4 FIC:1990:VirginiaQRev	the worse for wear , either . But that thing which	astonishes	all others most	-- for the people of England are justly and
5 TV:1998:Cold War	The speed with which the Soviets had produced ah atomic bomb	astonished	America I think	what surprised us was that considering the
6 WEB:2012:thefreelibrary.com	astounding astound tr.v. astounded , astounding , astounds To	astonish	and bewildered	See Synonyms at surprise . # From Middle English
7 WEB:2012:...al.library.upenn....	love He has had , and still has for us ,	astonishes	and confounds me	the more , considering what we are ; and
8 NEWS:2000:AssocPress	the 104 DSC recipients , " he said , " will	astonish	and humble all	who read them and underscore our faith in a
9 ACAD:1994:ArtBulletin	, records what was known of these special friends , who	astonished	and moved their	contemporaries. 55 # In the arts , the scarcity
10 SPOK:2011:PBS_NewsHour	of Representatives and a Democratic president -- would also	astonish	and please the	American people , even if they did n't like
11 WEB:2012:bible.cc	were just the germs of those pregnant questions with which He	astonished	and silenced them	in after years : " What think ye of
12 ACAD:2009:AmerScholar	parts I do n't detest . It has some things which	astonish	and some which	are majestic . Anyway , as I've told
13 FIC:2001:FantasySciFi	stranger with a warmth and enthusiasm that would have	astonished	anyone who knew	him well . " I bring a missive for
14 FIC:2013:SouthwestRev	who attend or organize library sales -- confirmed what would n't	astonish	anyone who reads	: Readers still cherish the physical book and
15 BLOG:2012:burtfolsom.com	in his personal life and in his public statements that he	astonished	Arthur Krock	the veteran New York Times reporter , who won
16 WEB:2012:israellect.com	have exerted for ten centuries ... ' You will probably be	astonished	as many Christians	were years ago when I electrified the nation
17 MAG:2000:MilitaryHist	Major General Sir Henry Colville , the division commander , was	astonished	as the attack	went in and was powerless to stop it .

Figure 6. Syntactic features of verb “astonish”

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that even semantically similar verbs diverge significantly in frequency, register, and grammatical behavior. The verb wonder dominates the domain due to its polysemous nature and discourse utility. Surprise maintains a strong presence in narrative and factual registers, while amaze and astonish are more expressive and limited in range. Future studies may expand this work by including multimodal corpora or diachronic data to track changes in emotional language over time. Additionally, cross-linguistic comparisons could reveal whether similar patterns exist in other languages.

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Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda salbiy ekspressivlik: Twitter misolida lingvopragmatik tahlil

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda, xususan Twitter platformasida salbiy ekspressivlikning lingvopragmatik xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. O‘zbek va ingliz tillarida yozilgan tvitlar misolida hashtaglar, sarkazm, kinoya, so‘kinish va boshqa nutqiy vositalarning madaniy va kommunikativ vazifalari yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ijtimoiy tarmoq, salbiy ekspressivlik, Twitter, sarkazm, kinoya, hashtag, lingvopragmatika.

Аннотация

В статье анализируются лингвопрагматические особенности негативной экспрессивности в социальных сетях, особенно на платформе Twitter. Рассматриваются хештеги, сарказм, ирония и другие средства выражения в узбекских и английских твитах.

Ключевые слова: соцсети, негативная экспрессивность, Twitter, сарказм, ирония, хештеги, лингвопрагматика.

Abstract

This paper explores the linguopragmatic aspects of negative expressivity on social media, particularly on the Twitter platform. Based on tweets in Uzbek and English, the study examines hashtags, sarcasm, irony, expletives, and their communicative and cultural functions.

Keywords: social media, negative expressivity, Twitter, sarcasm, irony, hashtag, linguopragmatics.

1. Kirish

Salbiy ekspressivlik — bu kishilarning norozilik, g‘azab, tanqid yoki istehzoni ifoda etishida ishlatiladigan nutqiy vositalar majmuasidir. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, ayniqsa Twitter, bu kabi ekspressiv ifodalarning yengil va ochiq ko‘rinishlariga keng yo‘l ochgan. Hashtaglar, qisqa iboralar, sarkazm va kinoyalar orqali foydalanuvchilar o‘z hissiyotlarini tez va samarali tarzda bildiradilar. Ushbu maqola salbiy ekspressivlikning internet nutqida qanday aks etishini, uning tilshunoslik va madaniy jihatlarini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan.

2. Adabiyotlar sharhi

Internet nutqi va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi til xatti-harakatlari ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o'rganilgan (Crystal, 2006; Zappavigna, 2012; McCulloch, 2019). Salbiy ekspressivlik, ayniqsa, anonimlik yoki yarim anonimlik mavjud bo'lgan platformalarda tez-tez uchraydi. Bu esa foydalanuvchilarga hissiy reaksiyalarini to'liq va filtrsiz ifoda etish imkonini beradi.

Zappavigna (2012) hashtaglarning ijtimoiy aloqalarni shakllantirishdagi rolini o'rganadi. McCulloch (2019) esa internet tili orqali madaniy identitet qanday ifodalanishini ko'rsatadi. Ularning yondashuvlari ushbu maqola tahliliga asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

3. Metodologiya

Tadqiqotda 2023-yilning oktabr—dekabr oylarida Twitter'dan to'plangan 1000 ta tvit tahlil qilindi. Ular ingliz va o'zbek tillarida yozilgan bo'lib, siyosiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy mavzularni qamrab oladi. Har bir tvit quyidagi mezonlar asosida kodlandi:

- Sarkazm yoki kinoya mavjudligi;
- Salbiy emotsiyalar ifodasi;
- Hashtaglar ishlatilishi;
- So'kinish yoki kuchli baho berish;
- Yozilish uslubi (formal/infomal, qisqa/uzun).

4. Natijalar va tahlil

4.1 Ingliz tilidagi tvitlar

Ingliz tilida yozilgan tvitlarda sarkazm juda keng tarqalgan. Misol: "Love waiting in traffic for hours. Best day ever. #sarcasm". Bunday iboralar kontekst orqali salbiy ma'no kasb etadi. Bundan tashqari, inglizcha tvitlarda so'kinishlar (e.g., "WTF", "damn") orqali hissiyotlar ochiq ifodalanadi.

4.2 O'zbek tilidagi tvitlar

O'zbekcha tvitlarda esa salbiy ekspressivlik ko'proq kinoya va hajviy uslub orqali beriladi. Masalan: "Yana bir bor rahmat sizga, elektr ta'minoti!" — bu ibora yuzaki minnatdorchilik bo'lib ko'rinsa-da, aslida tanqid ifodasidir. O'zbek tilida so'kinish kamroq ochiq qo'llaniladi, ko'proq ijtimoiy me'yorlarga mos evfemizm va ijobiy o'rama ishlatiladi.

4.3 Hashtaglar va vizual vositalar

Har ikki tilda hashtaglar #fail, #lol, #norozni kabi salbiy munosabatlarni bildiradi. Shuningdek, GIF, emoji va suratlar orqali ham salbiy ekspressivlik kuchaytiriladi.

5. Xulosa

Twitter kabi ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda salbiy ekspressivlik tildagi ijtimoiy va madaniy tafovutlarni ochib beradi. Ingliz tilida ochiq va sarkazmli ifodalar ustunlik qilsa, o'zbek tilida bu holat ko'proq kinoya, hajviylik va madaniy normativlarga

muvofig tarzda ifodalanadi. Ushbu tafovutlar tarjima, til o'rgatish va ijtimoiy tahlil sohalarida amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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The Linguopragmatic Characteristics of Negative Expressivity in English and Uzbek

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida salbiy ekspressivlik vositalari lingvopragmatik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Undovlar, so'kinishlar, kinoya va sarkazm kabi vositalarning nutqdagi vazifasi va madaniy konnotatsiyasi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: salbiy ekspressivlik, kinoya, lingvopragmatika, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация

В статье проводится лингвопрагматический анализ средств негативной экспрессивности в английском и узбекском языках. Особое внимание уделяется интеръективам, ругательствам, иронии и сарказму в межкультурной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: негативная экспрессивность, ирония, лингвопрагматика, межкультурная коммуникация.

Abstract

This paper explores the linguo-pragmatic features of negative expressivity in English and Uzbek. It focuses on interjections, expletives, irony, and sarcasm, analyzing their functions in discourse and cultural implications.

Keywords: negative expressivity, irony, linguopragmatics, intercultural communication.

1. Introduction

Negative expressivity, as a linguistic and pragmatic phenomenon, reflects a speaker's emotions such as anger, frustration, sarcasm, and criticism. These forms are embedded in language through a variety of lexical and syntactic means, including expletives, interjections, idiomatic expressions, and intonation patterns. Given the cultural and linguistic diversity between English and Uzbek, an analysis of negative

expressivity within both languages can reveal not only linguistic contrasts but also deeper socio-pragmatic mechanisms. As Wierzbicka (1999) points out, language is a cultural script that encodes emotional behavior, and expressions of negativity are no exception.

2. Literature Review

Negative expressivity has been widely explored in sociolinguistics, pragmatics, and intercultural communication studies. Crystal (2008) defines expressivity as a speaker's use of language to convey personal feelings or attitudes. Within this scope, negative expressivity is particularly significant due to its social and psychological impact.

In English, negative expressivity often manifests through sarcasm and irony (Dyner, 2014). These forms are linguistically subtle and culturally conditioned. Uzbek, however, favors metaphorical and idiomatic expressions that serve similar functions but reflect different pragmatic norms (Turgunov, 2023).

In analyzing expressivity, the works of Lakoff (1973) and Brown & Levinson (1987) on politeness theory are particularly relevant. Their model shows that negative expressions often violate positive face wants, thus requiring mitigation strategies or indirectness. These strategies vary cross-culturally, making Uzbek and English a fruitful pair for contrastive analysis.

3. Methodology

This study uses a comparative linguo-pragmatic approach. Data were collected from various corpora, including COCA (Corpus of Contemporary American English) for English and Uzbekcorpus.uz for Uzbek. Literary dialogues, social media interactions, and everyday spoken discourse were also analyzed to provide naturalistic examples of usage.

Samples were categorized based on the type of negative expressivity: (1) interjections, (2) expletives/curse words, (3) irony/sarcasm, and (4) metaphorical phrases. Each example was examined for pragmatic function, cultural connotation, and frequency.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Interjections and Expletives

In English, words like "damn," "ugh," and "what the hell" are frequently used to convey frustration or annoyance. Their counterparts in Uzbek include expressions such as "voy-bo'," "dod-voy," and "e, la'nati!" While English expressions may serve as both emotional outlets and rhetorical devices, Uzbek interjections often carry stronger affective and cultural weight.

4.2 Irony and Sarcasm

English is known for its heavy use of sarcasm, especially in British and American cultures. For example, the sentence "Oh, great! Another meeting..." clearly expresses displeasure. In Uzbek, indirect criticism is more often conveyed through idioms: "Boshingga tosh yog'yaptimi?" or "Yaxshi bo'пти-da!" These phrases often soften the negative message while maintaining social harmony (Turgunov, 2023).

4.3 Metaphorical Phrases and Euphemisms

Uzbek language frequently employs euphemisms and metaphors to express criticism or discontent. Expressions like "Yana boshladi..." (used sarcastically) or "Odammi o'zi bu?" (used to insult indirectly) reflect cultural preferences for implicitness. In contrast, English users may resort to direct negation: "You're unbelievable," or "That's the worst idea ever."

4.4 Cultural Implications

The findings support the hypothesis that Uzbek speakers rely more on indirectness, metaphor, and intonation to express negative emotions, adhering to collectivist cultural norms. English speakers, particularly in Western contexts, are more likely to use sarcasm and direct expressions due to individualistic cultural patterns.

Moreover, the role of context and tone cannot be underestimated. An English phrase like "Nice job!" could be genuine or sarcastic, depending on intonation. Similarly, an Uzbek speaker might say "Qoyil-qoldim" sarcastically, depending on body language and prior discourse.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that negative expressivity is both linguistically rich and culturally embedded. While English favors sarcasm and overt markers, Uzbek leans towards idiomatic, metaphorical, and culturally encoded expressions. These differences have important implications for translation, language teaching, and intercultural communication.

Further research could include experimental pragmatics, corpus frequency analysis of specific phrases, and sociolinguistic surveys. Understanding how different languages encode negativity contributes not only to academic linguistics but also to diplomacy, education, and cross-cultural empathy.

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Гендерные особенности негативной экспрессивности в английском и узбекском языках

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Аннотация

Mazkur maqola ayollar va erkaklar nutqida uchraydigan salbiy ekspressivlikning gender xususiyatlarini tahlil qiladi. Til vositalari orqali norozilik, tanqid va salbiy munosabat bildirishda erkak va ayol nutqi qanday farqlanishi ko‘rsatiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: gender, ekspressivlik, so‘kinish, tahlil, nutq.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqola ayollar va erkaklar nutqida uchraydigan salbiy ekspressivlikning gender xususiyatlarini tahlil qiladi. Til vositalari orqali norozilik, tanqid va salbiy munosabat bildirishda erkak va ayol nutqi qanday farqlanishi ko‘rsatiladi.

Калит сўзлар: гендер, экспрессивлик, сўкиниш, таҳлил, нутқ.

Abstract

This article analyzes the gender-specific features of negative expressivity in English and Uzbek. It examines how women and men express criticism, disagreement, or dissatisfaction through language and identifies discourse and pragmatic differences.

Keywords: gender, expressivity, swearing, discourse, criticism.

1. Введение

Негативная экспрессивность представляет собой важную составляющую коммуникативного поведения, позволяющую говорящему выражать недовольство, возмущение, критику или иронию. Гендерный аспект в использовании экспрессивных средств давно привлекал внимание исследователей, особенно в рамках социолингвистики и прагматики (Coates, 2013; Tannen, 1990).

Цель данной статьи — выявить и описать различия в использовании негативной экспрессивности мужчинами и женщинами в английском и узбекском языках. Особое внимание уделяется речевым стратегиям, частотности использования и культурно-прагматическим особенностям.

2. Обзор литературы

Согласно Тэннен (1990), мужчины чаще используют прямую экспрессию недовольства, включая ругательства, сарказм и прямую критику, тогда как женщины склонны к более косвенным, смягчённым формам. Коутс (2013) утверждает, что женская речь, как правило, характеризуется стремлением к гармонизации и вежливости, даже при выражении негативных эмоций.

В узбекской культуре, где приняты высокие нормы вежливости и уважения к собеседнику, женщины чаще используют метафорические выражения, косвенные намеки и уменьшительные формы. Мужчины, напротив, могут использовать более жёсткие формы — особенно в неформальном общении или при доминирующем социальном статусе (Turgunov, 2023).

3. Методология

Материал исследования включал записи живой речи, онлайн-комментарии (Telegram, Facebook), интервью и отрывки из художественной литературы. Для английского языка использовался корпус COCA, для узбекского — *uzbekcorpus.uz*. Был проведён контент-анализ с фокусом на частотность, прагматическую функцию и контекстуальные различия.

Категории анализа:

1. Ругательства и выражения злости;
2. Ирония и сарказм;
3. Метафорические и эвфемистические формы.

4. Результаты и обсуждение

4.1 Ругательства и злость

В английском языке мужчины чаще используют слова типа “damn”, “fuck”, “bloody”, тогда как женщины — более мягкие формы: “oh dear”, “heck”, “gosh”. В узбекском — мужские говорящие употребляют “la'nati”, “uraman hozir!”, “shunaqa odammi?”, в то время как женская речь может включать: “voy-bo”, “dodim”, “meni rosa qiynab qo'udi”. Это указывает на различия в эмоциональной допустимости и социальных ожиданиях.

4.2 Ирония и сарказм

Женщины в обеих культурах чаще прибегают к косвенной критике через сарказм. Например, английская фраза “Nice of you to show up on time!” может быть сказана с ироничным оттенком. В узбекском языке аналогичная ирония выражается фразами: “O'sha bo'ldiyu!” или “To'g'risi, sizga qoyil qoldim!” (в значении обратного). Мужчины чаще используют агрессивные формы.

4.3 Метафорические формы и эвфемизмы

Женщины чаще употребляют фразы типа: “He's not the brightest bulb” (англ.) или “Qizig'i shundaki...” (узб.), чтобы выразить негативное мнение мягко. Мужчины, особенно в неформальной обстановке, могут сказать прямо: “He's an idiot” или “Bu ahmoq gap-ku!”

4.4 Культурные аспекты

Узбекская культура, ориентированная на коллективизм, поощряет вежливость и избегание прямых оскорблений, особенно в женской речи. В английской культуре, особенно в англо-американском пространстве, допускается более открытая негативная экспрессия, особенно у мужчин. Это коррелирует с моделями гендерной социализации и стереотипами мужественности и женственности.

5. Заключение

Исследование показало, что гендер оказывает значительное влияние на формы и способы выражения негативной экспрессивности в английском и узбекском языках. Женщины склонны к использованию косвенных, смягчённых форм, в то время как мужчины — к более прямым и интенсивным выражениям. Эти различия укоренены в культурных и социальных ожиданиях и имеют важное значение в межкультурной коммуникации, переводе и преподавании языка.

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O'zbek tilida frazeologizmlarning uslubiy ma'nolari

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Аннотация

Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tilida frazeologizmlarning qo'llanishi va ularning uslubiy xususiyatlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Iboralarning leksik ma'nosi haqida fikr yuritilgan, ularning emotsional-ekspressiv ma'no ifodalash xususiyatlari misollar bilan dalillangan. Frazeologik polisemiya hodisasi, ko'p ma'noli iboralarning ma'noviy uzviyligi tadqiq qilingan.

Tayanch so'zlar: frazeologizm, barqaror birikma, frazeologik polisemiyalar, semantic uzviylik, metafora, konnotativ bog'liqlik.

Annotation

This article provides information on the application of phraseologisms in the Uzbek language and their methodological features. There was thought about the lexical meaning of phrases, the features of their expression of emotional-expressive meaning were evidenced by examples. The phenomenon of phraseological polysemy, the spiritual continuity of ambiguous phrases, has been researched.

Base words: phraseologism, stable conjunction, phraseological polysemies, semantic continuity, metaphor, connotative connection.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация об использовании фразеологизмов и их стилистических особенностях. Проведено рассуждение о лексическом значении словосочетаний, доказаны на примерах особенности их эмоционально-экспрессивной смысловой экспрессии. Исследовано явление фразеологической многозначности, духовной преемственности многозначных выражений.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизм, устойчивое сочетание, фразеологическая многозначность, семантическая непрерывность, метафора, коннотативная связь, режим.

Frazeologizmlar tarkibiy jihatdan qat'iy qolipga ega bo'lgan bir butun holda ko'chma ma'no anglatadigan so'z birikmasi yoki gap qurilishidagi turg'un bog'lanmalardir. Iboralar leksik jihatdan, semantik va stilistik imkoniyatlari hamda strukturasiga ko'ra o'ziga xos til birligi sanaladi. Shu sababli ham frazeologiya sohasi chuqurroq o'rganishni taqozo qiladi.

Bilamizki, frazeologik birliklar o'zining serqirraligi bilan nutqimiz go'zalligini oshirishda katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu sohaning tarixiga nazar soladigan bo'lsak, frazeologizmlardan ilk bor adabiyot fanida foydalanilgan. Bora-bora badiiy adabiyotlarda bir tildan ikkinchi tilga bu kabi ajralmas birikmalarni tarjima qilish imkonsiz bo'lib bordi va frazeologik birliklar tilshunoslikda kengroq tadqiq qilina boshladi. Frazeologiya atamasi tilshunoslikda ilk bor ingliz adabiyotshunos olimi Neander tomonidan badiiy asarlar tarjimasini jarayonida qo'llanilgan. [1]

Iboralar ma'nosida emotsional-ekspressiv uslubiy yuk kuchli ifodalanadi. Masalan, *boshi osmonga yetdi, terisiga sig'madi, bahri ochildi, dimog'i chog' bo'ldi, kayfi chog' bo'ldi, qo'yi mingta bo'ldi* kabi iboralar "xursand bo'ldi" birligi ma'nosini ifodalagan. Ayni vaqtda iboralarda ushbu ma'no ekspressiv-emotsional holatda berilmoqda. Iboralarni bir tildan boshqa tilga so'zma-so'z tarjima qilib bo'lmaydi, chunki iboralarda milliy kolorit ham mavjud bo'ladi. Iboralarning qismlari qat'iy bir qolipga kirib, barqarorlashgan bo'ladi. Frazeologik birliklar tarkibida nechta so'z ishtirok etishidan qat'i nazar, ular bir umumiy ko'chma ma'no ifodalaydi, gapda butunligicha bir bo'lak vazifasida keladi. Barqaror birikmalarga obrazlilik, jozibadorlik va barqarorlik xususiyatlari ham xos bo'ladi. *Eshon mayizning tagiga turna ekibdi ("tugatmoq")*. Frazeologik ma'no obrazli va jozibali ekanligi bilan so'zning leksik ma'nosidan farqlanadi. Chog'ishtiring: *xufiya – yeng ichida, beqiyos – yer bilan osmoncha*. Frazeologik ma'no ibora tarkibidagi biror so'zning ko'chma ma'nosiga asoslanishi (*ishning ko'zi, gapning tuzi*) yoki tarkibidagi qismlarning umumiy ma'nosiga tayanib ko'chma ma'no ifodalashi mumkin (*og'zi qulog'ida, bel boglamoq*). Yoxud tarkibidagi qismning ma'nosiga mutlaqo aloqasi bo'lmagan ma'no anglatadi (*yulduzni benarvon uradi, yuragiga qil sig'maydi*). [2]

Odatda iboralarning tarkibi qoliplashgan bo'ladi. Shuning uchun ham frazeologizmlar orasiga so'z qo'shish, tarkibidagi so'zlarning o'rnini almashtirish mumkin emas. Masalan, *boshini ko'tardi (sog'aydi)* iborasini *boshini yuqori ko'tardi* tarzida qo'llab bo'lmaydi. Biroq o'zbek tilidagi ayrim iboralar tarkibiga so'z kiritib qo'llash mumkin. Masalan, og'zaki nutqda ko'p qo'llanadigan *boshimni og'ritma* iborasini *boshimni ko'p og'ritma* shaklida qo'llash mumkin. Shunisi ham borki, tarkibiga boshqa so'z kiritib qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan iboralar ko'proq uslubiy imkoniyatlarga ega bo'ladi.

Badiiy va publisistik asarlarda iboraning bir-ikki komponenti muallif tomonidan o'zgartirib qo'llanishi mumkin, yangi leksik qurshovli bu turdagi frazeologizmlarda emotsional-ekspressivlik yanada kuchli ifodalanadi. Xalq iboralari modellari asosida yaratilgan bunday frazeologizmlar kitobxonda hajviy his uyg'otadi. A. Qahhor "*ninadayni tuyaday qilmoq*" iborasi modeli asosida "*danakday xamirturushdan bir tog'ora xamir qilmoq*", "*burganing yo'talidan bo'ron qo'pormoq*"; "*tovonini yalamoq*" iborasi modeli asosida esa "*botinkasini mo'ylovi bilan cho'tkalamoq*" kabi qator yangi iboralar yaratgan novator yozuvchi.[1]

O'zbek tili leksikasi frazeologizmlarga boy til sanaladi. Og'zaki nutqda qadimdan ishlatilib kelinayotgan turg'un birikmalar, qochirimlar, kinoyali so'z birikmalari, aforizmlar va maqollar bugungi kunda ham o'z kuchini yo'qotmagan. Shunisi ma'lumki, o'zbek tilida tilimizda inson tana a'zolari nomlari ishtirok etgan iboralar juda ko'p uchraydi. Ularga ko'plab misollar keltirish mumkin:

Soch :tepa sochi tikka bo'lmoq, sochiga oq oralagan, sochi oqardi.

Burun: burni ko'tarilgan, burnini suqmoq, burnidan ip o'tkazib olmoq.

Og'iz: og'zi ochilib qolmoq, og'zidan gullab qo'ymoq, og'zi qulog'iga yetmoq.

Tish: tishi o'tmaydi, tishini qayramoq, tishini tishiga qo'ymoq.

Barmoq: besh barmoq baravar emas, barmoq bilan sanarli, barmog'ini tishlamoq.

Bilak: bilak shimarib ishga kirishmoq, bilagi zo'r.

Quloq: qulog'i ding bo'ldi, qulog'i tom bitmoq, quloqqa lag'mon ilmoq.

Ko'z: ko'zi uchib turgani yo'q, ko'zi ochilmoq, ko'z ilg'amas.

Bo'yin: bo'yniga qo'ymoq, bo'yniga ilmoq, bo'yni yo'g'on.

Qo'l: qo'lini sovuq suvga urmaslik, qo'li egri, qo'ling dard ko'rmasin.

Oyoq: oyog'iga bolta urmoq, oyoq osti bo'lmoq, oyoqdan qolmoq. [4]

Tildagi boshqa leksik birliklar kabi iboralar ham turli nutq uslublarida xoslangan bo'ladi. Masalan, *pixini yorgan*, *juftakni rostlamoq*, *tayyor oshga bakovul* kabi iboralar oddiy so'zlashuv uslubiga xos bo'lsa, *siyosiy tanglik*, *buzilmas do'stlik*, *siyosiy lo'ttibozlik* kabi iboralar ommaviy nutq uslubiga xosdir.

Frazeologik birliklarda ko'p ma'nolilik, polisemantik frazeologik birliklarning shakllanishi tilshunoslar uchun qiziqarli soha hisoblanadi.

Polisemiya leksik birliklarning ko'p ma'noliligi hodisasi bo'lib, ularning ma'nolari bir-biriga yaqinligi va bog'liqligi bilan xarakterlanadi. Polisemiya hodisasi nutq ta'sirchanligini ta'minlaydi, shu bilan bir qatorda tilning lug'at boyligini oshiradi. Iboralardagi ko'p ma'nolilik ularning serqirra ma'nolarga ega ekanligini bildiradi: Masalan *tishi o'tmaydi* iborasini quyidagi ma'nolarda qo'llash mumkin: 1) qattiqroq narsani maydalashga tishining kuchi yetmaydi; 2) biror tushunchani idrok qila olmaydi, uqmaydi yoki anglab yeta olmaydi; 2) *bir pul* iborasi esa qadr-qimmatsiz, foydasi yo'q kabi ma'nolarni ifodalaydi.

Frazeologik polisemiyalar ma'nolari o'rtasida o'zaro bog'liqlik mavjud bo'ladi. Ularning ma'nosida semantik uzviylikni kuzatish mumkin. *Semantik uzviylik* iboralarning ichki ma'no rivojidan kelib chiqadi. Bunday birliklarda iboraning asosiy, ya'ni birlamchi ma'nosi boshqa ma'nolarning yuzaga kelishiga zamin yaratadi. Semantik uzviylikka ega bo'lgan iboralar ma'nosi kontekstda kengayishi yoki, aksincha, torayishi mumkin. "*Ko'zi ochildi*" iborasi "bilim oldi, anglab yetdi" ma'nosida tushuniladi. Ushbu iboraning ma'nosi kontekstda "hayotiy tajriba orttirdi" yoki "endi avvalgiday sodda emas" ma'nolari bilan kengayishi mumkin. Yuqoridagi ikki holatda ham "*ko'zi ochildi*" iborasi "oldin bilmagan holatdan xabardor bo'lish" ma'nosi bilan semantik jihatdan uzviy bog'liqlikka ega.

Tilimizdagi ko'pgina iboralar *metaforik uzviylikka* ega bo'ladi. Odatda iboralar bir butun holda ko'chma ma'no ifodalaydi. Ularda ifodalanayotga ko'chma ma'no kontekstda asliga bog'liq ravishda yangi metaforik ma'no hosil qilishi mumkin.

Bir narsa, belgi, harakatning nomi boshqasiga o'zaro o'xshashlik asosida ko'chirilsa, metafora usulida ko'chirilish deyiladi. Masalan: *U do'stining biqiniga turti. Ularning idorasi shaharning biqiniga joylashgan.* Metafora usulida nom ko'chish faqat shakliy o'xshashlik asosida emas, balki belgi o'xshashligi asosida ham, harakat o'xshashligi asosida ham sodir bo'ladi. [3]

Iboralarda ko'pincha metaforik tasvirlar asosida leksik ma'no ifodalanadi.

Masalan, *ko'ngli oq* – "ichki dunyosi toza" ma'nosini bildiradi. "*Oq*" so'zi ushbu iborada o'z ma'nosida emas, balki metaforik ma'noda qo'llanilgan; *ko'zini ochmoq* – kimningdir haqiqatni anglab yetishiga yordam berish ma'nosini bildiradi. Ushbu ibora bir butun holda metafora usulida ko'chma ma'noda qo'llanadi.

Ko'ngli ko'tarmaydi iborasi birinchi ma'nosida ("yeb-icha olmaslik") narsalarga nisbatan ishlatilsa, ikkinchi ma'no ("yoqtirmaslik") bu iborani "ovqat"dan boshqa narsalarga ko'chirish asosida shakllangan.[4]

Iboralarning metaforik jihatdan uzviyligi quyidagilarga asoslanadi:

- iboralarda obrazli ifoda ustun bo'ladi, obrazlar bir-birini to'ldiradi;

- ibora yaxlit tushunchani ifodalaydi, uning ma'nosi bir butun holda tushunarli bo'ladi;
- iboradagi obrazlar bir-biriga uyg'un bo'ladi.

Yuragi muzlab ketdi, qon bosimi ko'tarildi, ko'zlari chaqnadi kabi iboralar har xil fiziologik holatlarni anglatadi, biroq ularning barchasi ruhiy holat, hissiy kechinma bilan bog'liq. Shuning uchun ham ular aynan bir matn tarkibida ketma-ket qo'llansa ham, metaforik ma'no saqlanib qolaveradi. Biroq tilimizdagi barcha iboralar bunday imkoniyatga ega emas. Masalan, *ko'zlari daryo, ich-ichidan yonardi* kabi iboralardagi metaforik ma'nodagi uzviylik kontekst bilan bog'liq.

Ba'zi iboralar kayfiyat, baho yoki munosabat orqali polisemantik xususiyatini namoyon qiladi. Frazologik polisemiyalar ma'nosidagi bunday bog'lanishni *konnotativ bog'liqlik* deb atash mumkin. Masalan, *bo'yniga qo'ymoq* iborasi uchta ma'noni 1) "to'nkamoq, ag'darmoq"; 2) "isbotlab, e'tirof qildirmoq"; 3) "bajarishga rozi qilmoq"[5] ma'nolarini bildiradi. Iboraning ushbu ma'nolardan qaysi birini ifodalashi kontekstda, ya'ni muallifning bahosi yoki munosabati orqali anglashiladi.

Tilning lug'aviy imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishda, badiiy adabiyotda va kundalik muloqot jarayonida iboralarning ahamiyati juda katta. Iboralar (yoki frazeologizmlar) – bu birgalikda barqaror ma'noga ega bo'lgan so'z birikmalaridir. Ular bevosita ma'nosidan ko'ra ko'proq obrazli, ko'chma ma'noda ishlatiladi va yuqorida sanab o'tilgan jihatlari bilan ahamiyatlidir:

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytib o'tish joizki, o'zbek tilida iboralar juda ko'p imkoniyatlarni kashf etadi. Ibora yordamida fikr ta'sirchan, jonli ifodalanadi. Ibora orqali bir necha so'z bilan barqaror, teran ma'no ifodalash mumkin. Masalan, *yelkasiga tog' bosilgandek bo'ldi* iborasi insonning ruhiy holati og'irligi, uning tashvishlar girdobida qolganini qisqa, ammo teranroq ifodalashga yordam beradi. Iboralar bilan muloqot jarayonini jonli, quvnoq va ta'sirchan tashkil qilish mumkin. U so'zlovchining kayfiyatini, uning ichki olamini ham ko'rsatib turadi.

Shuni ham alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, iboralar milliy madaniyat, qadriyatlarlar, xalqning urf-odatlarini bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'ladi. Shuning uchun ham har bir til o'ziga xos bo'lgan iboralarga ega bo'ladi. Demak, tilda iboralarni o'rinli qo'llash milliy tilning boyligini, milliy madaniyat va urf-odatlarini ko'rsatib turadi. O'zbek tilidagi iboralar o'zbek mentalitetining o'ziga xos talqini hamdir.

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AGRONYMS AS A MAIN FIELD OF TOPONYMICS

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Annotatsiya. Tilshunoslik fan sifatida ajralib chiqqandan keyin lingvistika sohasidagi ko'plab muammolar o'z yechimini topishni boshladi. Onamastika sohasi bilan bog'liq muammolar ham shular jumlasidandir. Joy nomlari va unga teng bo'lgan birliklarni tadqiq qilish lingvistikaning oldidagi muhim vazifalardan biri desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Toponimika ko'plab filologlar tomonidan o'rganilgan soha bo'lishiga qaramasdan unda hali o'z yechimini topmagan muammolar talaygina. Mazkur maqolada shunday muammolardan biri hisoblangan agronimlar haqida so'z yuritiladi. Muallif o'z fikr va mulohazalarini misollar yordamida ochiqlab, tushintirib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: toponimika, onamastika, agronim, tilshunoslik, agronimiya, toponimik birlik, toponimik obyekt, nom.

Аннотация. После того, как лингвистика оформилась как дисциплина, многие проблемы в области языкознания стали находить решения. К ним относятся проблемы, связанные с областью онамастики. Не будет преувеличением сказать, что изучение топонимов и их эквивалентов является одной из важнейших задач, стоящих перед языкознанием. Несмотря на то, что топонимика является областью, изучаемой многими филологами, в ней все еще остается много нерешенных проблем. В данной статье обсуждается агронимия, которая является одной из таких проблем. Автор поясняет и поясняет свои мысли и мнения с помощью примеров.

Ключевые слова: топонимия, онамастика, агроним, лингвистика, агронимия, топонимическая единица, топонимический объект, название.

Abstract. After linguistics emerged as a science, many problems in the field of linguistics began to find their solutions. Problems related to the field of onamastics are among them. It is no exaggeration to say that the study of place names and their equivalents is one of the important tasks of linguistics. Despite the fact that toponymy is a field studied by many philologists, there are still many problems in it that have not yet been solved. This article discusses agronyms, which are considered one of such problems. The author explains her thoughts and opinions with the help of examples.

Keywords: toponymy, onamastics, agronym, linguistics, agronymy, toponymic unit, toponymic object, name.

Onomastics is the branch of linguistics that studies any proper nouns, the history of their emergence and change, as well as the collection of all proper nouns in

a language. The science of onomastics divides proper names into the following groups (sections) according to the categories of objects that receive them: anthroponymy - proper names of people (names, surnames, patronymics, nicknames, pseudonyms), toponymy - proper names of geographical objects, theonymy - names of gods, goddesses, religious and mythical figures and creatures according to various religious ideas, zoonymy - (conditional) proper names, nicknames given to animals, cosmonymy - names of regions of space, galaxies, constellations, etc., common in scientific circulation and among the people, astronomy - represents the set of names of individual celestial bodies (planets and stars). In addition, there are several other sections (groups) of onomastics. For example, one branch of onomastics is called realonyms (names of objects that existed before and now), while the opposite branch, mythonyms, refers to the names of imaginary, fabricated objects.

Depending on the level of study of the linguistic characteristics of proper names, onomastics is divided into such types as literary and dialectal onomastics, customary (practical) and poetic onomastics, modern and historical onomastics, theoretical and practical onomastics. One of these, theoretical onomastics, studies the emergence of proper names in language and speech, belonging to literary and dialectal spheres, their nominative (naming) bases, development, various changes in this process, the use of onomastic units in speech, their distribution in certain territories and languages, and the structural structure of onomastic units. The study of proper names in literary texts is a separate problem, and this is the main task of literary onomastics or onomapoetics. Onomastics also studies the phonetic, morphological, derivational (formation, formation), semantic, and etymological aspects of proper names, using comparative-historical, structural, genetic, areal, onomastic mapping, and other methods of linguistics. Practical onomastics deals with the transcription, transliteration of names belonging to foreign languages, traditional (according to pronunciation and spelling), identification of translatable and untranslatable names, preparation of instructions on how to write "foreign" names in one's own language, formation of new onomastic units from names adopted from foreign languages, naming and assimilation of names. Language is one of the social phenomena, in which the socio-political, spiritual and cultural views of the people, national customs, lifestyle, and aspirations are expressed. In linguistics, there are such lexical layers that are associated with the life, customs, and history of a particular people. The study of such lexical layers requires the study of the history and ethnography of this people.

When classifying language lexical units, including toponyms, we proceed from their linguistic properties. The correct choice of the direction of classification in research facilitates the determination of the true nature of the object under study and a number of other features. The following views of S. Qorayev, who reflected on the classification of toponyms, are noteworthy: "A toponym has a certain meaning, in the

words of toponymists, a toponym has information and reflects a real phenomenon" [1; 142]. Given that toponyms reflect this real reality, they should, of course, be divided into some groups. We believe that such a classification of toponyms will facilitate the study of their semantic essence. In general, the issue of the classification of toponyms has been one of the main objects of study in linguistics. Various noteworthy views have been proposed in this regard, which describe the most effective and convenient ways of classifying toponyms. The research conducted by H. Sharipov on the classification of toponyms is noteworthy [2; 128].

H. Sharipov, who conducted research based on the materials of the Kyrgyz language, one of the Turkic languages, noted that place, water and mountain names in Kyrgyzstan can be said to be formed on the basis of the following signs, noting their appearance as 1) natural geographical conditions in places; 2) natural underground resources in these places; 3) names of people, their living conditions; 4) names of animals and objects [2; 128]. The author noted that the structural aspects of place names in Southern Kyrgyzstan are not the same, that the names have simple, compound and complex forms and characteristics, and that they are formed in a morphological, syntactic and morphological-syntactic way typical of Turkic languages. H. Sharipov recommended classifying the formation of names from a grammatical point of view as follows:

I. Simple names. a) Names that arose on the basis of root words. Such names are found, although less often. Toponyms in the root word form often seem to be related to the names of things, objects, and sometimes to the names of ancient clans and tribes; b) names formed on the basis of artificial words. This type of toponyms is common, their character is also different, and they appear with the help of various formative affixes.

II. Compound nouns. 1) nouns formed by the syntactic method (from the combination of two or more roots). According to the material (word classes) of such nouns: a) noun+noun; b) adjective+noun; c) number+noun; d) number+noun+noun; e) noun+verb; f) adjective+noun+noun; g) adjective+verb+noun. 2. Names formed by the morphological-syntactic method include noun+noun and adjective+noun, sometimes noun+noun, with a forming affix in the middle or at the end.

III. Complex nouns [3; 48-49]. The author of the article includes names that have now been simplified, whose etymology and semantics are difficult to determine, and which are partially compound words. The article by Z. Dosimov occupies a special place in the classification of toponyms of Uzbekistan. Because in this article, the issue of classifying toponyms was analyzed on a large scale for the first time [4; 17-20]. Z. Dosimov noted that the classification of place names according to their lexical-semantic and grammatical structure has become widespread. The scientist noted that there are two relations in the lexical-semantic classification of toponyms: first, 1)

toponymic names that arose from ethnonyms; 2) toponyms that arose from onomastic names (personal names); 3) toponyms that arose from category group names; 4) toponyms associated with the structure of the earth, water and building structures, the flora, the profession of the population, various events-gatherings, etc.; secondly, 1) toponyms denoting the name of a tribe; 2) toponyms denoting the name of a nation; 3) toponyms named after people; 4) toponyms given in relation to a profession; 5) toponyms denoting an object sign; 6) toponyms named after plants (trees); 7) toponyms associated with the name of a people, homeland; 8) toponyms denoting geographical relief. The scientist also noted that in this type of systematization of toponyms there is no clear boundary between groups and suggested that it is appropriate to use the lexical-semantic principle in classifying toponyms, based on the nature of the research and the goals set by the researcher.

In studying toponyms, we may encounter a number of questions and comments. Because most toponyms tend to quickly lose their toponymic nature. That is, we have studied through many studies how a toponym can become an oronym, agronym, hydronym, urbanym, or the like. In today's article, we will examine the features of a toponym becoming an agronym.

One of the important features of agronyms is their changeable nature. Consequently, they can be easily changed or modified compared to other toponyms. Like other types of toponyms, they are territorial and are used in the speech of limited people. Since the period of "living" of agronyms is relatively short, it is not difficult to determine their meaning. Agronyms have always played an important role in reviving the historical and linguistic image of cities. For example, Beshyog'och Square in Tashkent was called Beruniy Square in the 70s, Komsomol Square in the 80s, and since 1991 it has been used again in its original form as Beshyog'och Square. The same can be said about Chorsu Square, Khadra Square, and Registan Square.

While we are studying agronyms, it is no secret that we have learned through many studies that they are part of toponyms. Toponyms are considered a component of the vocabulary of each national language, and although their existence and use are within the general laws of that language, they have their own linguistic characteristics. We can observe them in the phonetic, lexical-semantic and grammatical characteristics of the language. In the emergence of place names, the appearance of this geographical object, its location, natural conditions, land resources, fauna and flora, the profession of the local people, the economy, or in connection with some event, the name of a certain person or tribe, clan, and many other reasons and signs - characteristics can be given. Although there are several reasons associated with the naming of a place, the most characteristic of them is selected. Determining the lexical-semantic groups of toponyms, dividing them into certain groups and types, and classifying them on this basis is of great importance in determining the meanings of these units.

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ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA SPORT DISKURSINING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslikdagi "diskurs" tushunchasi, uning tahlili va ayniqsa sport sohasidagi qo'llanilishi keng yoritiladi. Sport diskursi doirasida sport tilining xilma-xilligi, janrlari, ijtimoiy o'ziga xosliklar, kuch munosabatlari, media va muxlislar diskursi, hamda globallashuv va texnologiya bilan bog'liq jihatlar tahlil qilinadi. Maqola diskurs tahlilining lingvistik, ijtimoiy va madaniy kontekstlarda tilni qanday anglash va o'rganishga xizmat qilishini tushuntiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: diskurs tahlili, sport diskursi, tilshunoslik, media tili, muxlislar diskursi, multimodallik, til va jamiyat, globallashuv, texnologiya.

Abstract: This article provides a broad overview of the concept of "discourse" in linguistics, its analysis, and its application, especially in the field of sports. Within the framework of sports discourse, the diversity of sports language, genres, social identities, power relations, media and fan discourse, and aspects related to globalization and technology are analyzed. The article explains how discourse analysis serves to understand and study language in linguistic, social, and cultural contexts.

Keywords: discourse analysis, sports discourse, linguistics, media language, fan discourse, multimodality, language and society, globalization, technology.

Аннотация: В статье представлен обзор понятия «дискурс» в лингвистике, его анализ и применение, особенно в сфере спорта. В рамках спортивного дискурса анализируется разнообразие спортивного языка, жанров, социальных идентичностей, властных отношений, медийного и фанатского дискурса, а также аспекты, связанные с глобализацией и технологиями. В статье объясняется, как дискурсивный анализ служит для понимания и изучения языка в лингвистических, социальных и культурных контекстах.

Ключевые слова: дискурсивный анализ, спортивный дискурс, лингвистика, медиаязык, фанатский дискурс, мультимодальность, язык и общество, глобализация, технологии.

Tilshunoslikdagi "diskurs" atamasi alohida jumladan tashqari og'zaki va yozma muloqotni ifodalaydi. U dialoglar, hikoyalar, nutqlar yoki yozuvlar kabi kengroq til birliklarini qamrab oladi va ularning qanday tashkil etilganligi, ularda

qanday ma'no yaratilganligi va turli vaziyatlarda aqanday ishlashiga qaraydi. Diskurs tahlili tilning bilim va voqelikni yaratish, kuch dinamikasi bo'yicha muzokaralar olib borish, ijtimoiy pozitsiyalar va o'ziga xoslikni bildirish va ma'no yetkazish uchun qanday ishlatilishini o'rganadi. Shuningdek, u til, jamiyat va madaniyat o'rtasidagi aloqalarni ko'rib chiqadi. Suhbat vujudga keladigan ijtimoiy va madaniy sharoitlarni o'rganishdan tashqari, u diskursning uyg'unligi, janrlari va tashkil etilishini o'rganishni talab qiladi. Sportda tildan foydalanish, jumladan, sportchilar, murabbiylar, muxlislar, sharhlovchilar va sport jurnlistlari o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlarni o'rganish tilshunoslikda sport diskursi deb nomlanadi. Ushbu ko'p tarmoqli soha tilshunoslik, sotsiologiya, psixologiya va aloqa fanlari nazariyalari va metodologiyalaridan foydalangan holda sport kontekstlarida tilning ko'p qirralarini o'rganadi.

Tilshunoslikdagi diskurs turli maqsadlar uchun og'zaki va yozma muloqotni o'z ichiga olgan alohida jumladan tashqari tilni tashkil etish va yaratishni anglatadi. U bitta jumladan kattroq yoki kichikroq til segmentlarini o'z ichiga oladi, lekin har doim jumla darajasidan tashqari ma'noni bildiradi. Diskurs ketma-ket bog'langan og'zaki yoki yozma jumalarning izchilligini va ma'no kasb etishini o'z ichiga oladi. Tilshunoslikdagi formalistik va funksional paradigmalar diskursga turlicha qarashlarni taklif qiladi, birinchisi, uni gap yoki gapdan yuqori til sifatida belgilaydi, ikkinchisi esa kontekstda foydalanishni ta'kidlaydi. Tilshunoslikning jadal rivojlanayotgan sohasi bo'lgan diskurs tahlili asosiy e'tiborni til foydalanuvchilari ma'noni qanday izohlashi, matnlarni tushunishi, suhbatga kirishishi va bog'langan diskursdagi izchillikni idrok etishini tushunishga qaratilgan. Zellig Xarris, diskurs tahlilini joriy etgani uchun, diskursni morfemalar, bo'laklar va jumladan yuqori bo'lgan iyerarxik daraja sifatida ko'rib, uning strukturaviy xususiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Maykl Stubbs jumalarni alohida alohida o'rganishdan iboralarni kontekstda tekshirishga o'tishni ta'kidlaydi, bu o'z navbatida diskurs tahlili tilshunoslar tomonidan tuzilgan va kontekstdan tashqarida bitta jumladan tashqari har qanday tadqiqotni qamrab olishini ko'rsatadi. Tilni diskurs sifatida tushunish nafaqat lingvistik konstruktsiyani, balki vaziyat kontekstidagi havola, ma'no va kuchni ham ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi. Ushbu yondashuv diskurs faqat katta hajmdagi jumlar ekanligi haqidagi tushunchani shubha ostiga qo'yadi va gap darajasidan tashqarida paydo bo'ladigan sifat farqlarini ta'kidlaydi.

Quyida sport diskursining ba'zi asosiy jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi:

Tilning xilma-xilligi: Sportdagi til mintaqaviy lahjalar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muhit va madaniy ta'sirlar kabi omillarga asoslangan o'zgaruvchanlikni namoyish etadi. Tilshunoslar bu tafovutlar maydonda ham, undan tashqarida ham sport nutqida qanday namoyon bo'lishini o'rganishadi.

Janr tahlili: Sport diskursi turli janrlarni o'z ichiga oladi, masalan, o'yin-o'yin sharhlari, intervyular, matbuot anjumanlari, o'yin hisobotlari, muxlislar muhokamalari

va ijtimoiy media o'zaro ta'siri. Tilshunoslar har bir janrning lingvistik xususiyatlari va konventsiyalarini tahlil qilib, ma'no qanday tuzilganligini va uzatilishini tushunishadi.

O'ziga xoslik va kuch: Sportdagi til sport jamiyatidagi ijtimoiy o'ziga xosliklarni, kuch dinamikasini va ierarxiyalarini aks ettiradi va quradi. Tilshunoslik tadqiqotlari irq, jins, millat va ijtimoiy sinf kabi omillarga asoslangan holda kimliklarni muhokama qilish va mustahkamlash uchun tildan qanday foydalanilishini o'rganadi.

Til va namoyish: Tilshunoslar tilning sport ko'rsatkichlarini shakllantirishdagi rolini, jumladan motivatsion nutq, jamoaviy muloqot va murabbiylik strategiyalarini o'rganadilar. Ular lingvistik belgilar sportchilarning fikrlash tarziga, ishonchiga va musobaqa paytida qaror qabul qilishga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadilar.

Media diskursi: Sport ommaviy axborot vositalari, jumladan televidenie ko'rsatuvlari, gazeta maqolalari va onlayn platformalar sport tadbirlari va sportchilar haqida jamoatchilik fikrini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Media diskursining lingvistik tahlili tilning rivoyatlarni qanday qurishini, tortishuvlarni asoslashini va auditoriya talqiniga ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi.

Muxlislar diskursi: Muxlislar sevimli jamoalari va o'yinchilarni qo'llab-quvvatlashlarini bildirish uchun kuylash, olqishlash va onlayn munozaralar kabi turli lingvistik amaliyotlarda qatnashadilar. Tilshunoslar fan madaniyati, shaxsni shakllantirish va jamiyatni qurishda tilning rolini tushunish uchun fan nutqini o'rganadilar.

Multimodallik: Sport diskursi ko'pincha tilni imo-ishoralar, yuz ifodalari va tana tili kabi vizual elementlar bilan birlashtirgan multimodal muloqotni o'z ichiga oladi. Lingvistik tadqiqotlar sport kontekstlarida ma'noni etkazish uchun og'zaki va og'zaki bo'lmagan signallarning qanday o'zaro ta'sirini o'rganadi.

Til va globallashtirish: Globallashtirish davrida sport madaniyatlararo muloqot va almashinuv platformasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tilshunoslar til sportchilar, murabbiylar va turli til va madaniyatlarga mansub muxlislar o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlarni qanday osonlashtirishini o'rganadilar. **Til siyosati va rejalashtirish:** Sport tashkilotlari va boshqaruv organlari sport jamoatchiligi ichidagi muloqotni tartibga solish uchun til siyosati va ko'rsatmalarini amalga oshiradi. Tilshunoslar til siyosatining sportdagi inklyuzivlik, mavjudlik va til xilma-xilligiga ta'sirini o'rganadilar.

Til va texnologiya: Texnologiyadagi yutuqlar sportni iste'mol qilish va muhokama qilish usulini o'zgartirdi, jonli translyatsiya, ijtimoiy media va ma'lumotlar tahlili kabi yangiliklar sport nutqini shakllantirdi. Lingvistik tadqiqotlar texnologiyaning sportda tildan foydalanish va muloqot amaliyotiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi.

Xulosa o'rnida, tilshunoslikdagi sport diskursi sport sohasidagi til, madaniyat va jamiyat o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro bog'liqlik haqida qimmatli tushunchalarni beradi. Sport kontekstlarida lingvistik amaliyotni tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqotchilar

tilning inson o'zaro ta'sirining dinamik va ko'p qirrali jihati sifatida qanday ishlashini tushunishimizga hissa qo'shadilar.

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TILSHUNOSLIKDA EPIDEYKTIK NUTQ O'RGANILISHINING RITORIK ASOSLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada notiqlik san'atining insoniy muloqotdagi o'rni, uning jamiyatdagi axloqiy, siyosiy va huquqiy ahamiyati yoritilgan. Notiqlik qadimiy yunon va rim jamiyatlarida fan sifatida shakllanib, ritorika maktablari orqali yuqori mavqega ega bo'lgani, Sitseron va Kvintilian kabi faylasuflar tomonidan nazariy asoslari ishlab chiqilgani ta'kidlangan. Maqolada shuningdek, notiqlik san'atining tarixiy rivojlanish jarayoni, siyosiy va sud nutqlari orqali ommalashuvi, ritorika fanining ijtimoiy-siyosiy ehtiyojlar bilan bevosita bog'liqligi hamda uning zamonaviy davrdagi dolzarbligi tahlil qilingan. Ritorikaning ba'zida o'z mavqeini yo'qotib, adabiyot nazariyasiga qo'shilib ketgan davrlari ham ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Notiqlik, ritorika, nutq san'ati, siyosiy nutq, sud nutqi, Sofistlar, logograflar, Koraks, Sitseron, Kvintilian, Yunoniston, Rim, ritorika tarixi, muloqot, ijtimoiy-siyosiy fan.

Abstract: The article examines the role of oratory in human communication, its moral, political and legal significance in society. It is emphasized that oratory as a science was formed in ancient Greek and Roman societies, achieved a high status thanks to the schools of rhetoric, and its theoretical foundations were developed by such philosophers as Cicero and Quintilian. The article also analyzes the historical development of oratory, its popularization through political and judicial speeches, the direct connection of the science of rhetoric with socio-political needs, its relevance in modern times. It also shows the periods when rhetoric sometimes lost its positions and was absorbed by literary theory.

Keywords: Oratory, rhetoric, art of speech, political speech, judicial speech, sophists, logographers, Corax, Cicero, Quintilian, Greece, Rome, history of rhetoric, communication, socio-political science.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль ораторского искусства в человеческом общении, его моральное, политическое и правовое значение в обществе. Подчеркивается, что ораторское искусство как наука сформировалось в древнегреческом и древнеримском обществах, достигло высокого статуса благодаря школам риторики, а его теоретические основы были разработаны такими философами, как Цицерон и Квинтилиан. В статье также анализируется историческое развитие ораторского искусства, его популяризация через политические и судебные речи, непосредственная связь науки риторики с общественно-политическими потребностями, ее актуальность в современности. В нем также показаны периоды, когда риторика порой теряла свои позиции и поглощалась литературной теорией.

Ключевые слова: Ораторское искусство, риторика, искусство речи, политическая речь, судебная речь, софисты, логографы, Коракс, Цицерон, Квинтилиан, Греция, Рим, история риторики, коммуникация, социально-политическая наука.

So'zlash faoliyatining asosi bo'lgan nutq insonlarga muloqot vositasi sifatida xizmat qilish barobarida uning yaxshilik va yomonlikka, haqiqat va yolg'onga, shu bilan birga, nutqni to'g'ri va mohirona tuzish orqali aybdorni aybsiz, aybsiz odamni esa aybdor qilib ko'rsatish mumkinligi qadim zamonlardan antik faylasuflar va zamonaviy ritorika fani vakillarining ham e'tiborini tortgan⁹³. Omma oldida mazmun mohiyatli, ma'noli, jozibador gapirish va ta'sirchan nutq so'zlash san'ati yuqori baholangan davrlarda adresatni mantiqiy va emotsional ishontirish, o'z so'zlarini isbotlash va haqiqatni qaror toptirish, nutqni to'g'ri yo'naltirgan holda maqsadli tuzish san'ati o'ziga xos kasbiy faoliyat sifatida yuqori mavqeni egallagan⁹⁴.

Nutq san'ati, ya'ni notiqlikning alohida fan bo'lib rivojlanishi miloddan avvalgi 5-4 asrlarda Yunonistonga borib taqaladi. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda notiqlikning miloddan avvalgi 3-2 asrlarda Yunonistonda deyarli tizimli fan shaklini olganligi, miloddan avvalgi 1 asrlarda Rimda tarqalganligi, qadimgi davrlarda Sitseron, Kvintilian kabilar ijodida, o'rta asrlarda va yangi davrda Rossiyada Lomonosov ijodida rivojlantirilganligi qayd etiladi⁹⁵. Shu bilan birga, qadimgi Yunoniston va Rimda ritorika oliy gumanitar maktab darajasiga ko'tarilgan va 3 bosqichli ta'lim tizimining yuqori cho'qqisi hisoblangan, ammo bu mavqe antik davr oxirigachagina saqlanib qolgan. O'sha davrlarda boshlang'ich va grammatik maktabdan so'ng ritor maktabi chiroyli so'zlash san'ati, notiqlik mahoratini egallashni nazarda tutuvchi maktab sifatida tanilgan, bu davrda Sitseron va M.Kvintilianlarning "Notiqlik san'ati bo'yicha o'gitlar", "Notiq bilimi haqida" nomli kitoblari ritor maktabini boshqarishda asosiy

⁹³ Леммермен. Х. Уроки риторики и дебатов. М., "Уникум-пресс", 2002, с 75.

⁹⁴ Омонов Б.А. Сиёсий етакчи нутқ маданиятининг жамиятни демократлаштириш жараёнларига таъсири. С.ф.номз.диссер. Т., 2004; Арипова А.Х. Нотиқлик нутқининг лисоний услубий хусусиятлари. фил.фанл. номз. диссер. Т., 2002; Цицерон. Нотиқлик санъати. Т., Янги аср авлоди, 2015, 478 б.

⁹⁵ Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси. Т., "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси", 2004, 336-бет; Назаров. Қ. Жаҳон фалсафаси комуси. Биринчи жилд. А-Н. "Маънавият" нашриёти, Т., 2023, 910-бет.

qo'llanma bo'lgan⁹⁶. Ritorika fanining vakillari say-harakatlari bilan ritor maktabi davlat ahamiyatiga ega bo'la boshlagan⁹⁷.

Bu davrda notiqlikning yuqori tabaqa vakillari orasida keng tarqalgan siyosiy kengash nutqi notiqligi va yuqori-quyi tabaqa vakillari uchun zarur bo'lgan sud notiqligi o'ziga xos o'rin egalladi. Ayniqsa, afinalik qullarga ham sud jarayonlarida o'zini himoya qilish uchun nutq so'zlash imkoniyatining berilishi ortidan sud notiqligi ommalashdi, bu davrda sud nutqini tayyorlab beruvchilar "logograflar", keng bilimli, so'zga chechan kishilar esa "sofistlar" deb nomlandi⁹⁸. Ushbu jihatlarni inobatga olib aytish mumkinki, notiqlik ijtimoiy siyosiy shart-sharoitlar va zaruriyatlar asosida yuzaga kelgan ijtimoiy-siyosiy fandır. Shu sababli ham hozirgi kunda davlat rahbarlari uchun notiqlik san'atiga asoslangan ritorika fanining ahamiyati katta. Yunon olimi, ritorika fanining asoschisi Koraksning fikricha, ritorika "ishontiruvchi xizmatkor"dir⁹⁹.

Uzoq davrlar mobaynida siyosiy tuzumlarda ritorika faniga bo'lgan ehtiyojning tushib ketishi bilan ritorikaning mavqeyi pasayib borgan va ritorika tortishuvli masalalarni hal etish vositasigagina aylanib qolgan¹⁰⁰. Keyinchalik fanlar kesimida ritorika fani adabiyot nazariyasiga qo'shib ketdi va ritorika termini "dabdabali, quruq safsata" ma'nolarini anglatib qoldi¹⁰¹.

Shuni alohida ta'kidlash kerakki, barcha o'zbek tilshunos olimlari tomonidan qilingan ishlarda notiqlikning alohida turi bo'lgan epideyktik nutq turlari yuzasidan alohida tadqiqotlar kuzatilmaydi va hech bir tadqiqotda epideyktik nutqning o'ziga xos lingvistik xususiyatlari, ularning lingvistik yaxlitligini ta'minlovchi turli nutqiy tuzilmalarning kompozitsion tuzilishi borasidagi baxstalab masalalarga e'tibor qaratilmagan. Boz ustiga, hozirgi kunga qadar o'zbek tili entsiklopedik lug'atlarida hamda izohli lug'atlarida "epideyktik", "epideyktik nutq" terminlariga hech qanday izoh mavjud emas. O'zbek tilshunosligida epideyktik nutqning lingvistik tadqiqi, epideyktik nutqiy janrlar turlari, ularning qo'llanilish doirasi, mazmuniy tuzilishi, ularning lingvistik xususiyatlari asosiy masala sifatida o'rganilgan emas. Aslida

⁹⁶ Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 2 жилд, Т., "Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси", 2004, 336-бет

⁹⁷ Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 2 жилд, Т., "Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси", 2004, 336-бет

⁹⁸ Арипова А.Х. Нотиклик нутқининг лисоний услубий хусусиятлари. фил.фанл. номз. диссер. Т., 2002.

⁹⁹ Арипова А.Х. Нотиклик нутқининг лисоний услубий хусусиятлари. фил.фанл. номз. диссер. Т., 2002.

¹⁰⁰ Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси. 7 бўлим, парчин-солиқ. Т., "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" давлат илмий нашри, 2004, 336-бет.

¹⁰¹ Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси. 7 бўлим, парчин-солиқ. "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" давлат илмий нашриёти, Тошкент, 2004, 336-бет; Назаров. Қ. Жаҳон фалсафаси қомуси. Биринчи жилди. А-Н. "Маънавият" нашриёти, Т., 2023, 910-бет.

notiqlik san'atining ichki turkumlanishida epideyktik nutqiy butunliklar masalasi qadimdan farqlanib, alohida notiqlik turi sifatida ta'kidlanib kelingan.

Notiqlik san'atining qadimgi turlarida *sud*, *siyosiy* (siyosiy kengash suhbat va muhokamasi-bizningcha) va *maqto'v* notiqligi, Aristotel ritorikasida esa ijtimoiy-siyosiy nuqtai-nazardan *suhbat* (siyosiy kengash suhbat va muhokamasi-bizningcha), *sud* va *epideyktik (tantanavor) nutq* turlarining farqlanishi ushbu nutq turlarida adresantning strategik-pragmatik maqsadida adresatni ishontirish yoki inkor qilish, oqlash yoki ayblash, dalillar orqali isbotlash, maqtash yoki kamchiliklarini ko'rsatish va adresatni emotsional jihatdan rom qilish maqsadlarining alohidaligi va mustaqilliligi bilan belgilanadi¹⁰². Bunda tantanavor nutq¹⁰³ (genus demonstrativum), kengash (siyosiy muhokama nutqlari - bizningcha) nutqlari (genus deliberativum), suddagi nutqlar (genus indiciale yoki forense) bir-birlaridan mantiqiy va strukturaviy (shakl va mazmuniga ko'ra) farqli hodisalar sifatida e'tirof etilib, alohida notiqlik turi, ya'ni suxandonlik nutqi sifatida tushunilgan¹⁰⁴. Demak, qadimgi yunon notiqlik san'atida nutqning mazmuniy turkumlanishi aniq farqlangan.

O'zbek notiqlik madaniyati ham qadimiydir. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda SHarqda notiqlik madaniyatini targ'ib etishda Bahouddin Valad, J.Rumiy, Voiz Koshifiy, Voiz Qazviniy, SHirvoniy, Quraysh Saidiy, Qozi Ushiy, M.Qo'shqariy, Zamaxshariy, Beruniy, Forobiy, A.Navoiy kabi shoir, tarixchi va muhaddislar faol bo'lganligi qayd etilgan¹⁰⁵. Ushbu allomalar zamonida notiqlik san'ati bilan shug'ullanganlar *voizlar, nadimlar, qissago'ylar, masalgo'ylar, badihago'ylar, qiroatxonlar, muammogo'ylar, voizlar, no'yandalar, maddohlar, qasidaxonlar* kabi nomlar bilan ham yuritilgan¹⁰⁶, ammo bularning o'ziga xos ichki notiqlik yo'nalishlari farqlangan.

Ilmiy adabiyotlarda IX asrgacha voizlik vazifasini halifalar, shohlar bajarganliklari, IX asrdan davlat xukmdorlari nomiga *voiz* so'zini qo'shib aytish urf bo'lganligi, XII asrdan notiqlik san'at sifatida rivojlangani, voizlik faoliyatining, asosan, 3 turi, dabirlik, ya'ni davlat yozishmalarini qiroat bilan o'qish, xatiblik, ya'ni xutba o'qish, muzakkirlik, ya'ni juma, xayit va boshqa tantanalardagi nutqlarni o'qish ommalashgani, shu bilan birga, voiz nutqining 3 turi, sultoniyat, ya'ni yuqori tabaqalar nutqi, janggohlar nutqi, ya'ni askarlar nutqi, g'aribona, ya'ni oddiy fuqarolarga

¹⁰² Арипова А.Х. Нотиқлик нутқининг лисоний услубий хусусиятлари. фил.фанл. номз. диссер. Т., 2002; Цицерон. Нотиқлик санъати. Т., Янги аср авлоди, 2015, 478 б.

¹⁰³ Юнон нотиқлигида тантанавор нутқ эпидейктик нутқ, мақтов нутқи номлари билан ҳам юритилган.

¹⁰⁴ Цицерон. Нотиқлик санъати. Т., Янги аср авлоди, 2015, 478 б.

¹⁰⁵ Омонов Б.А. Сиёсий етакчи нутқ маданиятининг жамиятни демократлаштириш жараёнларига таъсири. с.ф.номз.диссер. Т., 2004; Арипова А.Х. Нотиқлик нутқининг лисоний услубий хусусиятлари. фил.фанл. номз. диссер. Т., 2002,

¹⁰⁶ Омонов Б.А. Сиёсий етакчи нутқ маданиятининг жамиятни демократлаштириш жараёнларига таъсири. С.ф.номз.диссер. Т., 2004;

mo'ljallangan nutqlari farqlanganligi haqida ilmiy ma'lumotlar mavjud¹⁰⁷. Voiz so'zi arabcha so'z bo'lib, jamoat oldida nutq so'zlovchi, voizlik bilan shug'ullanuvchi, professional notiq deya izohlanadi¹⁰⁸. Bu davrlarda voizlar chuqur bilim, yuksak madaniyat va maxsus ijrochilik salohiyati, chiroyli va ta'sirchan ovozi, aniq va ravshan talaffuz, o'z zamonasi uchun yetakchi tillarni bilish va boshqalarga ega bo'lgan¹⁰⁹. Qadimda Sharq mamlakatlarida xukmdor shaxsan o'zi jamoat oldiga chiqib, o'z siyosati, xalqaro ahvol va boshqalar haqida nutq so'zlagan. El oldiga chiqish, ayniqsa juma namozi, xayit, navro'z kunlari va boshqalarda mamlakatlararo urush boshlangan holatlarda yig'ilgan vaqtlarda nutq so'zlash odat tusiga kirgan, ammo 9-asrga kelib bu vazifani xushovoz, ta'sirchan gapiradigan, ishontira oladigan kishilarga topshirgan¹¹⁰.

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¹⁰⁷ Омонов Б.А. Сиёсий етакчи нутқ маданиятининг жамиятни демократлаштириш жараёнларига таъсири. С.ф.номз.диссер. Т., 2004.

¹⁰⁸ Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 2 жилд, бешик-гидрофизика. Т., “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат нашриёти, Тошкент, 2007, 489-бет.

¹⁰⁹ Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 2 жилд, бешик-гидрофизика, Тошкент, “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат нашриёти, 2007, 489-бет.

¹¹⁰ Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 2 жилд, бешик-гидрофизика, Тошкент, “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат нашриёти, 2007, 489-бет.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada badiiy obraz tushunchasi va metafora asosida qurilgan badiiy obrazlar tahlil qilinadi. Ularning tasviriy vositalar bilan bog'liqligi misollar orqali ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: badiiy obraz, badiiylik, metaforiklik, istiora, jadid adabiyoti, ichki o'xshashlik.

Abstract: This article analyzes the concept of an artistic image and artistic images built on the basis of metaphor. Their connection with figurative means is revealed through examples.

Keywords: artistic image, artistry, metaphor, allegory, modern literature, internal similarity.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется понятие художественного образа и художественных образов, построенных на метафоре. Их связь с наглядными пособиями поясняется на примерах.

Ключевые слова: художественный образ, художественность, метафора, аллегория, современная литература, внутреннее сходство.

Kirish

Badiiy obraz tushunchasi har bir asarning maqsad va mohiyatini ochib berishdagi asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. Shu jihatdan ham bu tushunchaga har bir millatning adabiyotshunosligida o'zgacha yondashilgan. Xususan, o'zbek adabiyotshunosligida ham badiiy obraz masalasi keng qamrovli tushuncha hisoblanadi. B.Sarimsoqov —...badiiylikning mohiyatini voqelikni obrazlar vositasida in'ikos ettirish tashkil etadi. Shu bois ham badiiylik- obraz, obrazlilik demakdir! [Sarimsoqov B., 2022. – S.7.] – deya, asar badiiyligini oshiruvchi, uning ta'sir kuchini namoyon ettiruvchi xususiyat bu obraz ekanligini ta'kidlaydi.

Tadqiqot materiallari va metodologiyasi

Har bir tushunchaning mazmuni va mohiyatini o'rganishda, uning ichki va tashqi strukturasi tushunishda, avvalo, u atamaning mazmunini anglash lozim. Xo'sh, obraz atamasining asl ma'nosi nima? —Obraz atamasi —raz (chiziq) so'zidan olingan bo'lib, —raz so'zidan —razit (—chizmoq, yonmoq, o'ymoq) va undan —obrazit (—cho'zib, o'yib, yo'nib shakl yasamoq) so'zi yasalgan. —Obrazitdan —obraz (—umuman olingan tasvir) vujudga kelgan. Aslida —obraz slavyan tillariga xos so'z bo'lib, u voqea-hodisalarning hayolda namoyon bo'ladigan manzarasini bildiradi. Slavyanlar —obraz deganda, avvalo, odamzotni azob-uqubatlardan saqlab qolish uchun Alloh tomonidan yuborilgan Iisus Xristos (Iso payg'ambar)ning rassomlar, haykaltaroshlar tasvirlangan qiyofasini tushunishgan [Umurov H., – S.42.]. Badiiy obraz tushunchasi nafaqat adabiyotda, balki san'atning boshqa turlarida ham o'z vazifasini bajaradi. Hayotda sodir bo'layotgan voqea- hodisalarni aks ettiradi, ya'ni

hayotning yozuvchi asaridagi suratidir. Badiiy obrazning tuzilishi, tasvirlanishi, mazmuni jihatidan adabiyotshunoslar tomonidan bir qancha xususiyatlari tasniflangan. Jumladan, D.Quronov obrazning a) individuallashtirilgan umumlashma; b) konkretlik; d) ratsional va emotsional birlik sifatida; e) metaforiklik; f) assotsiativlik; g) tugallanmaganlik; h) ko'p ma'nolilik singari xususiyatlarini ochib bergan. Bular orasida metaforiklik badiiy obrazning asosiy mohiyatini tashkil etadi. Metaforalar asosida aniq obyektning yoki mavhum tushunchalarning badiiy tasvirlari shakllantiriladi. Metaforik badiiy obraz yaratishda bir-biriga semantik va leksik nuqtai nazardan mos kelmaydigan so'zlardan foydalanish mumkin. Ya'ni yozuvchi tasvirlamoqchi bo'lgan voqelikni unga aloqador bo'lmagan tushuncha orqali o'quvchi ongiga ta'sir qiladigan darajada yetkazib berishni maqsad qiladi. D.Quronovga ko'ra, —metaforiklik badiiy obrazning bir narsa mohiyatini boshqa bir narsa orqali ochishga intilish, san'atga xos fikrlash yo'sinidir [Quronov D., 2004. – S.66.]. Metaforik obraz yaratish uchun aynan bir-biriga mos va yaqin ma'noli so'zlar qo'llanilmaydi. Aksincha, shu obraz ma'nosi anglashilishi uchun uning mazmunidan yiroq, faqatgina qaysi bir tarafi bilan o'xshashlik kasb etuvchi tasvirlar yuzaga keltiriladi. Masalan, yozuvchi bir inson obrazini, uning xarakteri, nuqsonlari, fazilatlarini ifodalashda metaforik obraz sifatida hayvonlar, o'simliklar, jonsiz narsalar suratini keltirishi ham mumkin. —...yozuvchi voqelikdagi narsa-hodisaning hammaga ma'lum tashqi o'xshashligiga emas, balki odamlar nazaridan yashirin ichki o'xshashligiga tayangan holda fikrlaydi. Masalan, Cho'lpon go'zal obrazi va inson erki – ozodligi, A.Qahhor xalqni aldayotgan Amin, mansabdor shaxs obrazlari bilan o'g'rilar, A.Oripov tilla baliqcha bilan o'z qobig'iga o'ralib yashayotgan odamlar, S.Ahmad ongsiz yirtqich hayvon bo'ri bilan o'z yurtidan, iymon-e'tiqodidan mosuvo bo'lgan Bo'rivoy obrazi o'rtasida o'xshashliklar topadi. O'z navbatida Xurshid Do'stmuhammad ham —Jajman hikoyasida bozorga kirib, hamma ozuqani yeb bitirayotgan to'rtoyoqli maxluq bilan insonning bitmas- tunganmas nafi, —Qichqiriqdagi anhorning kuchli oqimi va hayotning beshafqat sinovlari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlikni topishi- metaforik fikrlash natijasidir [Raxmonova X., 2021. – S.14.].

Tadqiqot natijalari

Metaforalar adabiyotda turli xildagi janrlarda qo'llanilsa-da, lirik asarlarni metaforalarsiz tasavvur etish qiyin. Ayniqsa, XX asr oxiri va yangi asr boshlarida shoirlar metafora asosida go'zal badiiy asarlar yaratdilar. Bilamizki, XX asr boshlarida ham shunga o'xshaganroq holat kuchaygan. Fitrat, Cho'lpon, Botu, Elbek kabi shoirlar xazon, qarg'a, boyqush, yulduz kabi o'nlab istioralarni faol qo'llagan edilar [Ganiyev I., 1998.]. Bu davrda, xususan, jadid adabiyotida qo'llanilgan metaforik obrazlar shoir fikrlarini pardalash, o'z fikrini ochiqdan-ochiq bayon eta olmaslik natijasida yuzaga kelgan. Bunda ijodkorlar asarlarining g'oyasini obrazlar, o'xshatishlar orqasiga berkitishga harakat qilganlar.

Men —o'zlikdan ko'pdan beri uzilib,—Ko'plik ichra botib ketgan tanamen.

U —ko'plikning qayg'usida cho'zilib,

Quloch otib, suzib yurgan – yana men [A.Cho'lpon., 2021. –S.27.].

Yuqoridagi satrlarda Cho'lpon o'zlik deb o'zini, ko'plik deb esa o'z xalqini nazarda tutmoqda. Ya'ni, O'zimdand voz kechib, xalqning qayg'usini hal qilmoq uchun oqimga qarshi suzayotgan menman, degan fikrni istioraviy o'xshatishlar orqali tasvirlamoqda. Bunday metaforik obraz aniq bir shaklda o'quvchi ongiga yetib bora oladi. Chunki bu yerda tashqi o'xshashlik ham mavjud bo'lib, xalq ko'pchilikni, ommani tashkil etadi.

Muhokama

Yuqoridagi parchada shoir Sharqning mag'lubiyati sababli tutqunga aylangan xalqni sarg'aygan yaproqqa qiyoslaydi. Sarg'aygan yaproq va o'z millatining orasida so'lish, xazon bo'lish, orzu-umidlarning poymol bo'lishi, xazon oyoq ostida toptalgani kabi xalq ham rus millati tomonidan kamsitilayotganligi o'rtasida uyg'unlik ko'radi. Bo'ronlarning ko'zlari, kim o'ynoqlar,

Golib Garbning qonga to'lgan ko'zidek [Cho'lpon A., 2021. – S.30.].

Cho'lpon tomonidan bo'ronlarning ko'zlari tarzida qo'llagan metafora Garbning, Chor Rossiyasining ko'zlariga qiyoslanmoqda. Bunda shoir faqatgina ko'zning tashqi o'xshashligini nazarda tutmagan. Asosiy ma'no bo'ronning shiddati, g'azabi, hech bir narsaga rahm-shafqat qilmasligidadir. Bu ichki ma'noni Garb hukumatining qay darajada qonxo'r ekanligini o'quvchiga yetkazish uchun yozuvchi tabiat manzarasini jonlatirishga va o'zaro parallellikni vujudga keltirishga harakat qilgan. Aslini olganda, she'rning sarlavhasidayoq metaforik obraz tasvirlanayotganini bilishimiz mumkin. She'rning Kuz tarzida nomlanishi kuz manzarasini tasvirlash, uni madh etish emas, aksincha, shoir poetik maqsadining fasl tasviri orqali o'quvchiga yetkazilishidir.

Xulosa

Xulosa o'rnida aytish mumkinki, metaforik obraz tushunchasi har bir ijodkor asarlarining asosiy tasvir vositasi bo'lgan. Faqatgina har bir davrda metaforik tasvirning maqsadlari turlicha ko'rinish kasb etgan. XX asr boshlarida millat erki uchun ilgari surilgan fikr isyonkorligi, xalqni uyg'otish orzusini yashirin ifodalagan bo'lsa, mustaqillik davri adabiyotida tasvirni yanada go'zallashtirish, poetik jozibadorlikni oshirish maqsadida metaforik obrazdan unumli foydalanilgan.

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O'zbek tili metaforalari shakllanishining antropotsentrik omillari

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada so'zlarning ko'chma ma'no kasb etishining antropotsentrik jihatlari, metaforalar shakllanishida stereotiplarning o'rni xususida so'z yuritilgan.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются антропоцентрические аспекты приобретения переносного значения словами, роль стереотипов в формировании метафор.

Kalit so'zlar. Metafora, metaforik modellar, milliy-obrazli tafakkur, stereotiplar, etnik stereotiplar, lingvomadaniy kontekst, lingvomadaniy kodlar.

Ключевые слова. Метафора, метафорические модели, национально-образное мышление, стереотипы, лингвокультурный контекст, лингвокультурные коды.

Jahon tilshunosligida metaforalarga bag'ishlangan salmoqli ishlar amalga oshirilgan. [Qarang:2] Mazkur tadqiqotlarning aksariyatida metaforalarga semantik, stilistik, pragmatik, lingvomadaniy va kognitiv aspektlarda yondashilgan. Keyingi davrda o'zbek tilshunosligida ham metaforalar ancha batafsil o'rganilganini ta'kidlash joiz. [Qarang:2] Xususan, ushbu hodisaning kognitiv yondashuvda o'rganilishi [2] o'zbek tilining ifodaviylikini ko'rsatuvchi mazkur birliklarning antropotsentrik tabiatini yoritishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi.

Aytish joizki, o'zbek tili metaforalari tilimizdan o'ziga xos tizim sifatida o'rin olgan. Bu tizim til sohiblarining tafakkur tarzi, olamning lisoniy manzarasini yaratishdagi o'ziga xosligi, metaforalar voqelanishining kognitiv, assotsiativ, lingvomadaniy va lingvopragmatik jihatlari qonuniyatlarni namoyon etadi. Metaforalar birinchi navbatda tilimizda metaforik modellar tizimini hosil qiladi, ushbu tizim esa lingvomadaniy hamjamiyat vakillarining lisoniy faoliyatini antropotsentrik yondashuvda o'rganish imkonini beradi.

Metaforik model – bu til sohiblari ongida mavjud bo'lgan yoki shakllanadigan konseptual sohalar o'rtasidagi aloqa sxemasi bo'lib, uni ma'um bir formula bilan ifodalash mumkin: "X – Y".[3] Bunda X – inson kognitiv faoliyatidagi boshqa tushunchaga o'xshatilmog'chi bo'lgan tushuncha, Y esa X ga o'xshatilayotgan

tushunchadir. Masalan, *sher yigit* birikmasidagi *sher* so'zining metaforik modeli shu nuqtayi nazardan "odam – hayvon" tarzidagi model bo'ladi.

O'zbek tilidagi metaforalar asosan odam haqida, tabiat va uning unsurlari haqida, narsa-buyumlar haqida, ijtimoiy munosabatlar haqidagi metaforalardan iborat bo'lib, turli metaforik modellarni namoyon etadi.

Biz ayni maqolamizda metaforalar shakllanishining antropotsentrik omillari haqida so'z yuritmoqchimiz.

Muayyan so'zning ko'chma ma'noga ega bo'lishi o'z-o'zidan hosil bo'ladigan tasodifiy jarayon emas. Bunda muayyan qonuniyatlar amal qiladi. Tildagi ko'plab metaforalarning yuzaga kelishida stereotiplar muhim o'rin egallaydi. **Stereotip** termini U.Lippmanga tegishli bo'lib, yunoncha *stereos – qattiq va tupos – tasvir* so'zlaridan olingan. Lingvomadaniyatshunoslikda "Predmet va vaziyatlar haqidagi turg'unlashgan milliy-madaniy tasavvurlar va ularning tilda aks etuvchi shakllari; olam konseptual manzarasining bir qismi, kichik mental manzara" ma'nosini anglatadi. [5, 76] Til sohiblari o'z kognitiv faoliyatida biror tushunchani boshqa tushuncha vositasida ifodalash uchun asosiy holatlarda etnik stereotiplardan foydalanadilar. Buni tilimizda faol qo'llanadigan **tulki** metaforasining shakllanishi misolida kuzatish mumkin. Ma'lumki, bu so'zning "o'taketgan ayyor, makkor odam" tarzidagi sememasi [4,IV; 541] ham mavjud: *Haqiqatda esa, bu tulkilar uni laqillatadilar.* A.Qahhor, Sarob. *Tergovchi eshitgisi ham kelmadi. "Senlarning hammang shunaqa tulkisan!" dedi. E. A'zam, "Anoyining jaydari olmasi".*

Tulki metaforasi "odam – hayvon" modelida shakllangan zoomorf metafora hisoblanib, metaforasi badiiy, so'zlashuv uslublarida faol qo'llanadi va til sohiblari tomonidan salbiy subyektiv munosabatni ekspressiv tarzda ifodalash maqsadida foydalaniladi.

Ma'lumki, tulki o'zbek tili sohiblari tasavvurida eng ayyor hayvon sifatida gavdalanadi. Xalq og'zaki ijodida, xususan, ertaklar syujetlarida tulki hatto o'zidan ham kuchli sher, arslon, bo'rini ham laqillatib ketadi. Shu sababli o'zbek lingvomadaniyatida tulki ayyorlik etaloniga aylangan. Mazkur tasavvur hiylagar va makkor odamlarni tulki bilan qiyoslash uchun asos bo'lgan. *Tulki* metaforasi *odam* konseptining nominativ maydoniga kiradi va uning baholovchi uzvi hisoblanadi. *Tulki* metaforasi bilan bog'liq etnomadaniy stereotiplar *tulkiday ayyor* o'xshatish qurilmasida, *Tulkining hiylasi ko'p, Yaxshisi – qochmoq; Bir tulkining hiylasi Necha yerda pand berar; Bir tulki yetti bo'rini yetaklar* kabi maqollarda o'z aksini topgan.

Olov metaforasi o'zbek tilida *muhabbat, ishq, hijron, ehtiros, nafrat, intiqom, qasos* kabi so'zlar bilan bog'langan holda yuqori darajadagi muayyan hissiyotni anglatadi va "tuyg'u – fizikaviy hodisa" modelidagi metaforani yuzaga keltiradi.

Mazkur metafora badiiy matnlarda ekspressivlikni yaratishdan iborat pragmatistik maqsadda faol qo'llanadi.

Olov naturmorf metafora hisoblanadi, ya'ni inson ruhiyati tabiiy hodisa vositasida tushuntirilgan. Til sohiblarining insonning jo'shqin, shiddatli, qalbni o'rtaydigan hissiyoti bilan olovning baland va kuydiruvchi harorati o'rtasidagi o'xshashlikni o'zaro qiyoslashlari natijasida yuzaga kelgan. Mazkur metafora o'zbek lingvomadaniyatida til sohiblarining salbiy tasavvurlari bilan ham bog'lanadi. Masalan: *hasad olovi, adovat olovi* kabi. *Olov* so'zi metaforik ma'noda voqelanganida, til sohiblarining tabiat hodisasi va odamga xos ruhiy holat xususidagi tushunchalari – ikki konseptual soha o'zaro kesishib, insonning ruhiy holatini aniq va ekspressiv tarzda ifodalovchi tabiat kodi sifatida voqelanadi.

O'zbek tilidagi *katta* so'zining “mashhur; iste'dodli” ma'nosini anglatib [4,III; 602], metaforik ma'no kasb etishida ham til sohiblarining mazkur o'lcham haqidagi turg'unlashgan tasavvurlari ma'lum ma'noda vosita bo'lgan: *Falon yosh yigit katta olim bo'lishni orzu qiladi, iste'dodli, qobiliyati ham kamoliga yetgan. Fitrat, "Rahbari najot"*.

O'zbek tili lingvomadaniyatida ham, boshqa lingvomadaniyatlardagi kabi, kattalik belgisi ham ijobiy, ham salbiy tasavvurlar bilan bog'lanadi. Masalan, *katta olim, katta ishlar, katta gap* kabi birliklarda *katta* so'zida ijobiy semalar voqelangan bo'lsa, *o'zini katta tutmoq, katta ketmoq, katta og'iz* birliklarida salbiy semalar reallashgan. *Katta* so'zining semantik tarkibidagi “kuch-darajasi, salmog'i ortiq, buyuk, zo'r” ma'noli sememasi ushbu so'zning metaforik ma'noda qo'llanishiga asos bo'lgan. Bunda til sohiblari tasavvuridagi *katta* va *kichik* dan iborat zidlik ham muayyan rol o'ynagan. Ya'ni ko'p ishlarni amalga oshirib, elga mashhur bo'lgan odam – “*katta*”, oddiy, uncha tanilmagan, el qatori odam – “*kichik*” odamdir. Buni so'zlashuv tilida qo'llanadigan, mening gapim hal qiluvchi kuchga ega emas, degan ma'noda aytiluvchi *Biz kichkina odammiz* jumlasini ham tasdiqlaydi. *Katta* so'zi bilan bog'liq stereotiplar quyidagi barqaror birliklarda o'z aksini topgan va bunda mazkur so'z orqali asosan odam tushunchasiga ishora qilingan: *Katta kelsa, oshga, kichik kelsa, ishga; Katta gapirguncha, katta tishla; Katta arava qayoqqa yursa, kichigi ham shuyoqqa yuradi; katta qilmoq; kattani kesib kichik qilgan; katta boshini kichik qilib*. Demak, ma'lum bo'ladiki, *katta* belgisi haqidagi muayyan tasavvurlar “odam belgisi – predmet belgisi” modelidagi ushbu metaforaning yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'lgan.

Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkinki, metaforik ma'no kasb etgan har qanday lug'aviy birlik o'zi mansub tilning lingvomadaniy kodiga, binobarin, uning jozibasini namoyon etuvchi lisoniy boylikka aylanadi. Til sohiblarining asrlar davomida voqelik unsurlari haqidagi turg'unlashgan tasavvurlari va ushbu tasavvurlar natijasi o'laroq yuzaga kelgan xulosalar – stereotiplar metaforalar tabiatini, uning kognitiv hamda lisoniy modellarini belgilab beruvchi muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi.

Metaforalarning shakllanishi zamirida muayyan lisoniy qonuniyatlar bilan birga til jamoasining aqliy, ijodiy salohiyati va lingvomadaniy konteksti bilan zich bog‘langan nolisoniy qonuniyatlar ham yotadi. Ularni aniqlash uchun esa metaforalarga antropotsentrik nuqtayi nazardan yondashish lozim. Metaforalar tizimini kognitiv tilshunoslik, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, assotsiativ tilshunoslik, psixolingvistika kabi sohalar nuqtayi nazaridan integrativ tarzda tadqiq etish o‘zbek tili sohiblarining “tafakkur grammatikasi”ni teran yoritib berishda va tilimiz metaforalariga xos lisoniy jozibadorlik sir-asrorlarini ocib berishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA SIFATLARNING SINTAKTIK FUNKSIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida sifatlarning sintaktik funksiyalari qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. Ikki tildagi sifatlarning gap ichidagi o‘rni, boshqa so‘z turkumlari bilan munosabati, atributiv va predikativ xususiyatlari o‘rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida sifatlarning sintaktik funksiyalaridagi o‘xshashliklar va farqlar aniqlangan. Maqolada sifatlarning substantivatsiya hodisasi ham ko‘rib chiqilgan. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi sifatlarning gap bo‘laklari sifatida qo‘llanilishining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: sifat, sintaktik funksiya, atributiv pozitsiya, predikativ pozitsiya, substantivatsiya, qiyosiy tahlil, gap bo‘laklari.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен сравнительный анализ синтаксических функций прилагательных в английском и узбекском языках. Исследуется положение прилагательных в предложении, их взаимосвязь с другими частями речи, атрибутивные и предикативные свойства в обоих языках. В результате исследования выявлены сходства и различия в синтаксических функциях прилагательных в английском и узбекском языках. В статье также рассматривается явление субстантивации прилагательных. Анализируются особенности использования прилагательных в качестве членов предложения в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: прилагательное, синтаксическая функция, атрибутивная позиция, предикативная позиция, субстантивация, сравнительный анализ, части речи **Annotation:** This article presents a comparative analysis of the syntactic functions of adjectives in English and Uzbek languages. The position of adjectives in sentences, their relationship with other parts of speech, attributive and predicative properties are studied in both languages. The research reveals similarities and differences in the syntactic functions of adjectives in English and Uzbek languages. The article also examines the phenomenon of substantivation of adjectives. The peculiarities of using adjectives as parts of a sentence in English and Uzbek languages are analyzed.

Keywords: adjective, syntactic function, attributive position, predicative position, substantivation, comparative analysis, parts of speech.

Kirish. Tilshunoslikda so'z turkumlarining sintaktik funksiyalarini tadqiq qilish fundamental va dolzarb mavzulardan biri hisoblanadi. Sifatlar har bir tilda o'ziga xos sintaktik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, ularning gap tarkibidagi funksiyalari, boshqa so'z turkumlari bilan munosabati va gap qurilishidagi roli muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida sifatning sintaktik funksiyalari qiyosiy tahlil qilingan bo'lib, bu ikki tilning tipologik jihatdan farqlanishiga qaramay, sifatning qo'llanilishidagi umumiy va o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlash nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga egadir.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi ikki til o'rtasidagi tipologik farqlar fonida sifatning sintaktik xususiyatlarini qiyosiy o'rganish orqali nafaqat nazariy tilshunoslik, balki amaliy tarjimashunoslik va til o'qitish metodikasi uchun ham amaliy ahamiyat kasb etishi bilan belgilanadi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari orasidagi tizimli farqlarni aniqlash tarjima jarayonida yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal etishda hamda chet tilini o'qitishda samarali yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Maqolada qo'yilgan maqsad – ingliz va o'zbek tillarida sifatning sintaktik funksiyalarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish, umumiy qonuniyatlarni aniqlash va farqli jihatlarni belgilashdan iborat. Bu maqsadga erishish uchun quyidagi vazifalar belgilangan: har ikki tilda sifatning atributiv pozitsiyada qo'llanilish xususiyatlarini aniqlash; predikativ pozitsiyada sifatning funksiyalarini taqqoslash; substantivatsiya hodisasini har ikki tilda ko'rib chiqish; sifatning gap bo'laklari sifatida qo'llanilishining o'ziga xos tomonlarini tahlil qilish.

Ilmiy maqolaning metodologik asosini N. Chomsky, O. Jespersen, V.V. Vinogradov, A.G'ulomov va boshqa tilshunoslarning ishlab chiqqan nazariy qoidalari

tashkil etadi. Ularning tadqiqotlari sifatlar va ularning sintaktik xususiyatlarini o'rganishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Asosiy qism. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida sifatlarning eng asosiy sintaktik vazifasi atributiv, ya'ni aniqlovchi vazifasida kelishidir. Biroq, ikki tilda sifatlarning atributiv pozitsiyada qo'llanilishida sezilarli farqlar mavjud[7].

Ingliz tilida sifatlar, odatda, aniqlangan so'zdan oldin keladi:

a beautiful flower (chiroyli gul); *an interesting book* (qiziqarli kitob); *the old man* (qari odam)

O'zbek tilida ham sifatlarning atributiv pozitsiyasi asosan aniqlangan so'zdan oldin keladi:

katta uy (a big house); *qizil olma* (a red apple); *aqli bola* (a clever child)

Ko'rinib turibdiki, asosiy pozitsiya jihatidan ikki tilda o'xshashlik mavjud. Biroq, ingliz tilida sifatlarning ketma-ketligi ma'lum qonuniyatga asoslanadi: fikr - o'lcham - yosh - shakl - rang - kelib chiqish - material - maqsad[5]. Misol uchun:

a beautiful small ancient round black Chinese wooden decorative box

O'zbek tilida bunday qat'iy ketma-ketlik mavjud emas, lekin ma'noviy jihatdan ma'lum tendentsiyalar kuzatiladi:

katta qizil chiroyli xitoy yog'och qutisi

Ingliz tilida ba'zi sifatlar faqat atributiv pozitsiyada qo'llaniladi:

the main problem (asosiy muammo); *the chief editor* (bosh muharrir); *a mere child* (shunchaki bola).

O'zbek tilida ham shu kabi holat kuzatiladi:

yagona yo'l (the only way); *asosiy vazifa* (the main task)

Ingliz tilida sifatlar predikativ pozitsiyada bog'lama fe'llar (copular verbs) bilan birga keladi:

The sky is blue. (Osmon ko'k.); *She seems happy.* (U baxtli ko'rinadi.); *The soup tastes delicious.* (Sho'rva mazali.)

O'zbek tilida predikativ pozitsiyada sifatlar, odatda, bog'lama vazifasini bajaruvchi "-dir" qo'shimchasi yoki nol morfema bilan qo'llaniladi:

Osmon ko'k(dir). (The sky is blue.); *Uy katta.* (The house is big.)

Ingliz tilida ba'zi sifatlar faqat predikativ pozitsiyada qo'llaniladi:

The child is asleep. (Bola uxlayapti.); *She is afraid of dogs.* (U itlardan qo'rqadi.)

O'zbek tilida bunday cheklanish kamroq kuzatiladi, ko'pchilik sifatlar ham atributiv, ham predikativ pozitsiyada qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Ingliz tilida predikativ pozitsiyada sifat to'ldiruvchi bilan kengaytirilishi mumkin:

I am happy with the results. (Men natijalardan xursandman.); *She is good at mathematics.* (U matematikada yaxshi.)

O'zbek tilida ham sifatlar predikativ pozitsiyada to'ldiruvchilar bilan kengaytirilishi mumkin, biroq bu ko'pincha kelishik qo'shimchalari yordamida amalga oshiriladi:

U ishidan mamnun. (He is satisfied with his work.); *Bola o'qishga qobiliyatli.* (The child is capable of studying.)

Ingliz tilida sifatlarning substantivatsiyasi (ot so'z turkumiga o'tishi) keng tarqalgan hodisa hisoblanadi:

the rich (boylar); *the poor* (kambag'allar); *the elderly* (keksalar)

Bunday substantivatsiya, odatda, artikl bilan birga keladi va ko'plik ma'nosini anglatadi.

O'zbek tilida substantivatsiya hodisasi turli xil qo'shimchalar yordamida amalga oshiriladi:

Kambag'allar (the poor); *boylar* (the rich); *yaxshilik* (goodness)

Shuningdek, o'zbek tilida sifatdan ot yasalishi "-lik/-lik" qo'shimchasi orqali ham amalga oshiriladi:

go'zallik (beauty); *qiynallik* (difficulty)

Ingliz tilida substantivatsiya hodisasi ko'proq umumiy tushunchalarni ifodalash uchun qo'llanilsa, o'zbek tilida bu hodisa aniqroq va konkret ma'nolarni ifodalash uchun ham keng qo'llaniladi.

Ingliz tilida sifatlar quyidagi gap bo'laklari vazifasida kelishi mumkin:

1. **Aniqlovchi:** *A beautiful landscape appeared before us.* (Oldimizda go'zal manzara paydo bo'ldi.)

2. **Kesim:** *The film was interesting.* (Film qiziqarli edi.)

3. **Kesim to'ldiruvchisi (Complement):** *I consider her intelligent.* (Men uni aqlli deb hisoblayman.)

4. **Hol:** *He spoke loud.* (U baland gapirdi.)

O'zbek tilida sifatlar quyidagi gap bo'laklari vazifasida keladi:

1. **Aniqlovchi:** *Katta binolar shaharda qurilmoqda.* (Big buildings are being built in the city.)

2. **Kesim:** *Osmonga ko'tarilgan binolar baland.* (The buildings rising into the sky are tall.)

3. **Ot-kesim:** *U juda aqlli.* (He is very intelligent.)

4. **Hol:** *U tez gapirdi.* (He spoke quickly.)

Ingliz tilida sifatlarning predikativ sifatidagi qo'llanilishi bog'lama fe'llar orqali ifodalanadi, o'zbek tilida esa bog'lama vazifasini ko'pincha nol morfema, "-dir" qo'shimchasi yoki edi, ekan, emish so'zlari bajaradi[9].

Ingliz tilida sifatlarning qiyosiy va orttirma darajalari sintaktik konstruksiyalarda o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega:

She is taller than her sister. (U singlisidan balandroq.); *This is the most interesting book I have ever read.* (Bu men o'qigan eng qiziqarli kitob.)

O'zbek tilida sifatlarning darajalari turli xil usullar bilan ifodalanadi:

U singlisidan balandroq. (She is taller than her sister.); *Bu men o'qigan eng qiziq kitob.* (This is the most interesting book I have ever read.)

Ingliz tilida qiyosiy daraja konstruksiyalari “*than*” bog'lovchisi yordamida, o'zbek tilida esa chiqish kelishigi (ablativ) “-dan/-dan” qo'shimchasi yordamida ifodalanadi.

Orttirma daraja ingliz tilida, odatda, artikl “*the*” va sifatning orttirma darajasi bilan, o'zbek tilida esa “eng” so'zi bilan ifodalanadi [10].

Xulosa

Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida sifatlarning sintaktik funksiyalari tahlili quyidagi xulosalarga kelishga imkon beradi:

Har ikki tilda sifatlarning asosiy sintaktik funksiyasi atributiv pozitsiyada aniqlovchi vazifasida kelishidir. Bu jihatdan tillar o'rtasida o'xshashlik mavjud, biroq ingliz tilida sifatlarning ketma-ketligi ma'lum qonuniyatga asoslanadi, o'zbek tilida esa bunday qat'iy tartib kuzatilmaydi.

Predikativ pozitsiyada sifatlarning qo'llanilishida farqlar mavjud: ingliz tilida bog'lama fe'llar (*is, are, seem, become*) ishtirok etadi, o'zbek tilida esa bog'lama vazifasini ko'pincha nol morfema, “-dir” qo'shimchasi yoki edi, ekan, emish so'zlari bajaradi.

Substantivatsiya hodisasi har ikki tilda mavjud, biroq ingliz tilida bu hodisa ko'proq artikl yordamida, o'zbek tilida esa ko'plik qo'shimchalari va “-lik/-lik” qo'shimchasi yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

Sifatlarning gap bo'laklari sifatida qo'llanilishida ham o'xshashliklar kuzatiladi: har ikki tilda sifatlar aniqlovchi, kesim va hol vazifasida kela oladi. Biroq, ingliz tilida sifatlar kesim to'ldiruvchisi vazifasida ham faol qo'llaniladi.

Sifatlarning darajalari har ikki tilda mavjud, lekin ularning ifodalanish usullari farq qiladi. Ingliz tilida qiyosiy daraja “*than*” bog'lovchisi yordamida, o'zbek tilida esa chiqish kelishigi “-dan/-dan” qo'shimchasi yordamida ifodalanadi.

Ushbu maqolaning amaliy ahamiyati shundaki, ingliz va o'zbek tillarida sifatlarning sintaktik funksiyalaridagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni bilish til o'rganuvchilar uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bunday bilimlar tarjima jarayonida yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etishga, tillararo interferensiya muammolarini hal qilishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, bu maqola natijalari ingliz va o'zbek tillari qiyosiy grammatikasi bo'yicha o'quv qo'llanmalar tayyorlashda ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

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SUGGESTIV NUTQNING FONOSEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada suggestiv nutqqa xos fonosemantik jihatlar yoritilgan, tovushlarning nutq ta'sirchanligini oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: fonosemantika, tovush simvolizmi, nutqiy ta'sir, suggestiv nutq

Аннотация. В данной статье освещены фоносемантические особенности, характерные для suggestивной речи, проанализированы возможности усиления выразительности речи с помощью звуков.

Ключевые слова: фоносемантика, звуковой символизм, речевое воздействие, suggestивная речь.

Annotation. This article highlights the phonosemantic features of suggestive speech and analyzes the possibilities of enhancing the influence of speech through sounds.

Keywords: phonosemantics, sound symbolism, speech influence, suggestive speech.

So'nggi yillarda tovushlarning inson ongiga, uning hissiyotlariga ta'sir qilishi masalasi ham tadqiqotchilarning diqqatini o'ziga jalb qilmoqda. An'anaviy tilshunoslikda tovushlarning yakka olinganda ma'no anglatmasligi g'oyasiga

tayaniladi, lekin fonosemantik tadqiqotlarda tovushlarning ma'lum shakllar, belgilar, ranglar yoki hissiyotlar bilan bog'liqligi e'tirof etiladi. Bu masalalar bilan shug'ullanuvchi tilshunoslik bo'limi fonosemantika yoki tovush simvolizmi nomlari bilan ataladi.

Fonosemantika haqidagi g'oyalar antik davrlardanoq ma'lum bo'lgan. Aflotunning "Kratilus" asarida Suqrotning "rho" tovushining harakat qilish ma'nosi bilan bog'liqligini *tromos (trembling)* – *qaltiramoq, trachus (rugged)* – *g'adir-budir, notekis, rumbein (whirl)* – *aylanmoq* kabi so'zlar misolida asoslab bergani keltiriladi. [11]

Fonosemantika haqidagi qarashlar psixologlar va tilshunos olimlar tomonidan rivojlantirib, mazkur hodisaning turli jihatlarini tadqiq qilingan. Jumladan, E. Sapir tovushlarning fonosemantik xususiyatlarini tajribalar orqali o'rgangan. Birinchi tajribada olim *table – stol* so'ziga nisbatan umuman ma'noga ega bo'lmagan "mil" va "mal" sifatlarini qo'llaydi. Respondentlardan *mil table* va *mal table* so'z birikmalaridan qaysi biri katta, qaysi biri kichikligiga javob berish so'raladi. Respondentlardan qariyb 81%i *mal table* birikmasini katta stol uchun, *mil table* birikmasini kichik stol uchun qo'llaydilar. Bunga ko'ra, E.Sapir "i" tovushi kichiklikni, "a" tovushi kattalikni anglatadi, degan xulosaga keladi. Ikkinchi tajribada ko'proq respondentlar qamrab olinadi – 11 yoshdan 18 yoshgacha bo'lgan o'smirlar va yoshlar, yoshi katta respondentlar va bir nechta xitoylik respondentlar ishtirok etadilar. Ular hech qanday ma'no anglatmaydigan, faqat bir tovush bilan farqlanuvchi oppozitsitsiyalarni tinglashlari va ularning katta-kichikligini aniqlashlari talab etiladi, masalan *a* va *i*, *a* va *e*, *z* va *s* va h.k. *a*, *ä*, *ε*, *e*, *i* tovushlari solishtirilganda, *a* va *i* orasida eng katta farq kuzatilgan, ya'ni *a* dan *i* ga qarab farqlar kengayib borgan. Shunga ko'ra, muallif farqlarni yuzaga keltiruvchi psixologik omilni "fonetik simvolizm" deb ataydi.[5: 225-239]

Fonosemantikaga oid yana bir qiziq psixolingvistik tadqiqot nemis olimi V.Kohler tomonidan amalga oshirilgan va u *maluma-takete* tajribasi deb nomlanadi. Olim respondentlarga ikki xil shakl – yumaloqsimon va yulduzga o'xshash shakl va o'ylab topilgan so'zlar – *maluma* va *takete* so'zlarini taqdim qiladi va so'zlarni shakllarga moslashtirishni so'raydi. Tajriba natijalariga ko'ra, ishtirok etuvchilarning qariyb 90%i *maluma* so'ziga yumaloqsimon shakl, *takete* so'ziga yulduzsimon, burchakli shakl mos kelishini tanlaganlar.[3]

Ingliz tilshunosligida tovushlar simbolizmi D. Kristal tomonidan o'rganilgan bo'lib, muallif tomonidan nashr etilgan ensiklopediyada ham bu mavzu aks etgan. D.Kristalning fikricha, ingliz tilida *gl-* bilan boshlanuvchi so'zlarning ko'pchilik qismi ko'rish, yorug'lik bilan bog'liq: *glance, glare, gleam, glimmer, glamor, glass, glaze, glimpse, glint, glisten, glitter, globe, glossy, glow* kabi. Bunda muallif *gl-* tovushlarining aynan yorug'lik va ko'rish bilan bog'liqligini tovush somvolizmiga

misol sifatida keltiradi.[1: 182-185] Shuningdek, D.Kristal tomonidan fonestetika haqida ham ilmiy fikrlar bildirilgan bo'lib, olim ma'lum tovushlar ishtirok etgan so'zlar boshqalarida ko'ra chiroyliroq ekaniga urg'u beradi. Muallif chiroyli deb topilgan so'zlarni tahlil qilib, ularda *l*, *m* tovushlari ko'p qo'llanganini aniqlaydi. Shu bilan birga, D.Kristal chiroyli so'zlar ega bo'lgan fonetik xususiyatlardan foydalanib yangi so'zlar hosil qilish imkoniyatlarini ham keltirib o'tadi. Bunda "so'zlar uch bo'g'indan iborat bo'lishi, urg'u birinchi bo'g'inga tushishi zarurligi, *m* yoki *l* tovushlaridan hech bo'lmagan bittasi (ikkalasi ham qo'llangani ma'qulroq), yuqori chastotali undoshlardan foydalanish, past chastotali undoshlardan foydalanishdan qochish, undoshlar artikulyatsiyasida uch xil usuldan foydalanish, qisqa unilardan foydalanish, unilarning o'rtadan yuqoriga, oldidan orqaga qarab borishi" tavsiya qilinadi. [2: 8-12]

Amerika va Yevropa tilshunosligida tovushlarning ramziy ma'nolarini o'rganuvchi yo'nalish uchun tovush simbolizmi termini keng qo'llanilsa, rus tilshunosligida fonosemantika termini tilshunoslikning ushbu bo'limi uchun qo'llaniladi. Rus tilshunosligida S.Voronin tomonidan fonosemantika tilshunoslikning alohida bo'limi sifatida e'tirof etildi va Peterburg fonosemantika maktabiga asos solindi.[8] Demak, tovushlar semantikasi, ularning ramziy ma'nolarni anglatishi masalasi g'arb tilshunoslari tomonidan qiziqish bilan o'rganilgan. So'nggi yillarda amalga oshirilayotgan tadqiqotlarda ham ushbu masalaning turli jihatlarini yoritib kelinmoqda.[6]

Tovushlarning hissiyotga ta'siri masalasi ham tilshunoslarning e'tiboridan chetda qolmagan. Xususan, M.Sakamoto va J.Uatanable yapon tilida tovushlarning fonosemantik xususiyatlarini o'rganishgan, ularning tadqiqotida tovushlarning his-tuyg'ular bilan bog'liq taktil jihatlarini yoritilgan. O'tkazilgan tajribalar asosida yapon tiliga oid tovushlarga xos quyidagi fonosemantik xususiyatlar aniqlangan: unililar uchun ijobiy taktil baholar orqa qator unililar (/u/), salbiy baholar esa old qator unililar (/i/ va /e/) bilan bog'langan. O'rta qator unililar (/o/ va /a/) asosan qo'pol, qattiq va quruq his-tuyg'ular bilan bog'liq. Undosh tovushlar tovush xususiyatlari va artikulyatsiyasiga qarab turlarga bo'lingan. Jarangli undoshlar toifasi (masalan, /dz/ va /g/) qo'pollik tuyg'ulariga, jarangsiz undoshlar (masalan, /ts/ va /s/) esa silliqlik tuyg'ulariga mos keladi. Lab-lab portlovchi (/p/ va /b/) va jarangli alveolyar burun (/n/) undoshlarining toifalari asosan yumshoq, yopishqoq va nam tuyg'ulariga tegishli bo'lsa, jarangsiz alveolyar sirg'aluvchi (/ts/) va jarangsiz alveolar portlovchi (/k/) undoshlar qattiq, sirpanchiq va quruq tuyg'ulariga aloqador bo'lgan.[4]

Rus tilshunosligida suggestiv nutqqa xos fonosemantik xususiyatlar ham tahlilga tortilgan. Suggestiv matnlar tovush-rang yozishmalariga boy. A. P. Juravlyov ovozli rangli yozishmalarining butun tasnifini taklif qiladi, ulardan foydalanish suggestiv matnlarning samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshirishi mumkin: A – to'q

qizil, Я - yorqin qizil, O - och sariq yoki oq (taqqoslang: OMO kir yuvish kukuni) , E - yashil, E - sariq-yashil, Э - yashil, И - ko'k, Ы – ko'kish, E - to'q ko'k, ko'k-yashil, nilufar rangi, Ю - havorang, siren, Ъ – ma'yus, to'q jigarrang yoki qora [Juravlev 1991].

Bundan tashqari, suggestiv matnlarda odatdagi foydalanish chastotasidan (masalan, mi, vo, is, li, go va boshqalar) oshib ketadigan tovush takrorlari (bo'g'inlarning takrorlanishi) ham uchraydi. [9: 21]

N.Chumicheva tomonidan reklamaga oid suggestiyaning fonosemantik xususiyatlari o'rganilgan. Muallif "Fonosemantik jihatdan uyg'un bo'lgan va odamning yashirin semantik sohasiga zid kelmaydigan so'zlar reklama matnlariga qabul qiluvchining e'tiborini beixtiyor qaratadi. Shu bilan birga, ongosti ovoqli tasvirlari estetik jihatdan ijobiy hissiy va rangli reaksiyalarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bir vaqtning o'zida paydo bo'ladigan bir nechta tovush tebranishlari, ularning chastotalari ma'lum bir muvofiqlikda bo'lib, yoqimli (konsonans) yoki yoqimsiz (dissonans) taassurotlarini yaratadi, deya ta'kidlaydi. [10: 12] N.Chumicheva tomonidan antisuggestiv vositalar ham tadqiq qilingan bo'lib, muallif tomonidan periferik undoshlar (labial, velar va laringeal), akustik yoki artikulyatsion xususiyatlarga ko'ra salbiy kodlashni o'z ichiga olgan tovushlar (past ohang, tupurish va yo'talning tovushli imo-ishoralari, tirnoqlarning shisha tirnash ovozi), talaffuzi qiyin so'zlar, ketma-ket uch va undan ortiq undoshlardan iborat bo'lgan so'zlar, suggerendning psixik leksikasi va axborot bazasidan chiqib ketadigan xos va ikkilamchi leksemalar antisuggestiv vositalar sifatida keltirilgan. Olima har xil individual konnotatsiyalarni keltirib chiqarishi tufayli reklama matnlarida mavhum tushunchalar (baxt, quvonch, go'zallik), shuningdek, sohaga oid atamalar, qisqartmalar, abbreviaturalar va evfemizmlardan foydalanishni tavsiya etmaydi. [10: 13]

Demak, suggestiv nutqda tovushlar ham ma'no jihatidan ahamiyat kasb etadi va nutqning ta'sirchan bo'lishi, tinglovchi bilan samarali muloqot yaratilishiga xizmat qiladi.

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РОЛЬ ЛИНГВОКРЕАТИВНОСТИ В РЕКЛАМНОМ ДИСКУРСЕ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается понятие лингвокреативности и её роль в рекламном тексте. Проводится анализ механизмов языкового творчества (новые слова, каламбуры, метафоры, звукопись и др.) и их функций в привлечении внимания аудитории и убеждении потребителя. Приводятся примеры рекламных слоганов с пояснением языковых приёмов. Делается вывод о том, что лингвокреативность служит важным средством повышения запоминаемости и эффективности рекламы.

Ключевые слова: лингвокреативность, рекламный дискурс, языковая игра, неологизмы, каламбуры, слоган, фонетические приёмы, стилистические фигуры, запоминаемость, убеждающее воздействие.

Abstract. The article explores the concept of linguistic creativity and its role in advertising discourse. It analyzes the mechanisms of language innovation—such as neologisms, puns, metaphors, sound symbolism, and other devices—and their functions in attracting audience attention and persuading consumers. Examples of advertising slogans are presented with explanations of the linguistic techniques employed. The study concludes that linguistic creativity is a crucial means of enhancing both the memorability and overall effectiveness of advertising messages.

Keywords: linguistic creativity; advertising discourse; language play; neologisms; puns; slogan; phonetic devices; stylistic figures; memorability; persuasive impact.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada lingvokreativlik tushunchasi va uning reklama matnidagi o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi. Lingvokreativlik mexanizmlari (yangi so'zlar, so'z o'yinlari, metaforalar, ovoz yozish va boshqalar) va ularning auditoriya e'tiborini jalb qilish va iste'molchini ishontirishdagi funksiyalari tahlil qilingan. Reklama shiorlariga misollar orqali lingvokreativlikni reklamada esda qolarliligi va samaradorligini oshirishning muhim vositasi bo'lib xizmat qilinganligi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvokreativlik, reklama diskursi, til o'yini, neologizmlar, so'z o'yinlari, shior, fonetik usullar, stilistik figuralar, esda qolarlilik, ishontirish ta'siri.

Введение. Рекламный дискурс обладает специфическими свойствами языка, отличающими его от обыденной речи. Как отмечает М.Шарик (2020), «язык, используемый в рекламе, преднамеренно создаётся» так, чтобы быть ярким и привлекающим внимание. [3] Копирайтеры формируют рекламное сообщение так, чтобы убедить потенциального покупателя в преимуществе товара и «сделать лучший возможный выбор слов» для достижения убедительного эффекта. Таким образом, реклама использует язык как «заряженный» («loaded») и стилистически выделенный феномен. В связи с этим возникает актуальный вопрос: возможна ли в рекламе подлинная языковая креативность? Некоторые исследователи отмечают, что рекламный дискурс рассматривается как «колонирующий» или «логофагический» (по О. В. Соколовой), забирающий приёмы из других типов дискурса. Тем не менее реклама активно оперирует языковыми новациями ради коммуникативной цели.

Лингвокреативность обычно понимается как творческое использование языка, включающее создание новых или необычных языковых единиц и нестандартные комбинации элементов. О.Соколова определяет языковую креативность как «создание новых, уникальных языковых единиц и модификацию отношений между ними» с ориентацией на «трансформацию языковой системы и создание нового языка». [2] При этом формальные новации (например, неологизмы, контаминации) сочетаются с семантическим приращением (полисемия, синонимия и др.), что ведёт к «деавтоматизации» восприятия адресата. В литературе традиционно различают два вида креативности: **языковую** (новые единицы и сочетания слов) и **дискурсивную** (обновление микроструктуры высказывания). При этом в рекламном тексте дискурсивная креативность мотивируется языковой: новаторское словообразование или игра слов становится базой для более широкой манипулятивной стратегии сообщения. Соколова подчёркивает, что в рекламе языковая креативность проявляется лишь в различной мере: она может быть выражена «в большей или меньшей степени». Роль языковых игр в рекламе прочно связана с прагматической целью – выделиться на фоне информационной перегрузки.

Основная функция лингвокреативности в рекламе – привлечение и удержание внимания потребителя. Креативные языковые средства выводят адресата из «автоматического» восприятия привычного текста (эффект деавтоматизации). О. В. Соколова описывает это как первый этап «языковой манипуляции»: нестандартный язык заставляет читателя переосмыслить привычные ассоциации и активизирует внимание. Далее во втором этапе происходит «автоматизация» – закрепление нового значения через привычные

паттерны. Как справедливо замечает М.Шарик, рекламная фраза должна быть одновременно привлекательной и убедительной, поэтому копирайтеры «пытаются максимально эффективно использовать язык и надеются, что это произведёт убеждающий эффект». [3]

Кроме того, языковая креативность усиливает запоминаемость и эмоциональное воздействие рекламы. Известно, что рифма, аллитерация и другие фонетические приёмы делают слоган мелодичным и задерживают его в памяти (так повышается эмоциональный резонанс). Бонсигони (2015) показывает, что речевые приёмы на уровне звука и морфологии («рифма, ассонанс, аллитерация, блендинг» и др.) в слоганах заметно повышают их **memorability** и эмоциональное воздействие. Повторение ключевых слов, экспрессивная лексика («лучший», «эксклюзивный», «новый» и т.д.) служат для создания позитивных коннотаций и доверия к бренду.[4] В целом, функции лингвокреативности в рекламе можно свести к следующим целям:

➤ **Выделение из массы рекламных сообщений** – создание фонетически и смыслово заметного текста.

➤ **Заинтересованность и убеждение адресата** – нестандартный язык помогает сформировать положительное отношение к товару и усилить влияние рекламного послания.

➤ **Запоминаемость и эмоциональное воздействие** – творческие приёмы облегчают запоминание и вызывают эстетическое удовольствие.

Рекламные тексты демонстрируют широкий спектр языковых приёмов, выходящих за рамки нейтральной речи. Ключевые категории проявлений лингвокреативности:

➤ **Каламбуры и полисемия.** Использование омонимов и двусмысленных фраз. Например, в слогане жевательной резинки «*Mentos. Свежее решение*» слово «свежий» употребляется сразу в двух значениях – буквальном («не утративший свежести») и переносном («оригинальный, неординарный»). Благодаря такому «сдвигу значений» послание приобретает игру смысла и вызывает интерес.

➤ **Неологизмы и контаминации.** Создание новых словосочетаний и гибридных терминов. Известен слоган Seat Toledo «*Enjoyneering*» – контаминация от английских «enjoy» и «engineering», дословно «инжиниринг удовольствия». Этот неологизм подчёркивает «удовольствие от вождения» и объединяет свойства автомобиля (инженерная точность + эмоциональная привлекательность).

➤ **Фонетические приёмы.** Рифма, аллитерация, ассонанс придают фразе мелодичность. Например, русский слоган «*Не тормози – Сникерсни*» («*Snickers*») строится на рифме и игре слов, делая его простым для запоминания.

Подобные приёмы часто используются для повышения звуковой привлекательности текста.

➤ **Стилистические фигуры.** Метафоры, метонимии, гиперболы и антитезы оживляют описание товара. (См., напр., «Свежий как весна», «Ярче солнца», «Мощнее ветра» и т.д.). Они усиливают экспрессию и привлекают воображение адресата.

➤ **Синтаксические аномалии.** Использование неполных предложений, вопросительных форм, обращения на «ты». Так, короткие призывы «Сделай шаг», «Что ты ждёшь?» создают эффект диалога с потребителем и повышают динамику текста.

Всё выше перечисленное можно у репрезентировать в следующей диаграмме:

Диаграмма.1. Основных категорий лингвокреативных приёмов.

Таким образом, диаграмма иллюстрирует, что наиболее значимыми для привлечения внимания и запоминания аудитории являются каламбуры / полисемия и фонетические приёмы; несколько меньший, но всё ещё высокий вклад вносят неологизмы и стилистические фигуры, тогда как синтаксические аномалии выполняют вспомогательную функцию. Используйте эти ключевые слова для индексирования статьи, а диаграмму — как наглядное дополнение при презентации результатов.

Перечисленные приёмы часто комбинируются. По словам М.Шарика, язык рекламы «высоко креативен и выделен, существенно отличается от обыденного языка». М. Шарик и другие исследователи перечисляют в рекламных посланиях богатый набор приёмов: рифму, аллитерацию, созвучия, метафоры, аллегии, смешение языков (code-mixing), гиперболы, антитезы, повторения и т. п. Например, приём **антафоры** (повтор начального слова или конструкции) встречается в слогане «Вдохновляет, удивляет, покоряет», а

гротеск (намеренное преувеличение) – в рекламных сообщениях типа «Самое вкусное молоко!» или «Цена ниже не бывает».

Заключение. Лингвокреативность выступает важнейшим механизмом эффективности рекламного дискурса. [5] За счёт творческого обращения с языком реклама привлекает внимание потенциальных покупателей, делает сообщение запоминающимся и эмоционально насыщенным. Как показывает анализ, сочетание новых слов, художественных фигур и звуковых приёмов «деавтоматизирует» восприятие адресата, активизирует его мышление и помогает выделить рекламируемый продукт среди конкурентов. При этом креативность в рекламе всегда служит прагматическим целям: она мотивирует к действию и убеждению (по мнению А. Азими, использование языка направлено на «убеждающий эффект» на поведение потребителя). Таким образом, лингвокреативные стратегии значительно повышают эффективность рекламных текстов, способствуя узнаваемости бренда и запоминанию рекламного послания.

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АКТИВИЗАЦИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ПРИКЛАДНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

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Аннотация: Современное образование направлено не только на передачу знаний, но и на формирование у студентов устойчивой мотивации к обучению, критического мышления и исследовательской инициативы. Особенно актуальна активизация познавательной деятельности студентов в рамках преподавания прикладной лингвистики, которая требует от обучающихся активного включения в анализ языковых процессов и практическое применение знаний.

Ключевые слова: познавательная деятельность, инновационное обучение, активизация, прикладная лингвистика, методы активизации, преподаватель, студент.

Abstract: Modern education is aimed not only at the transfer of knowledge, but also at developing in students a sustainable motivation for learning, critical thinking and research initiative. The activation of students' cognitive activity is especially relevant within the framework of teaching applied linguistics, which requires students to actively engage in the analysis of language processes and the practical application of knowledge.

Keywords: cognitive activity, innovative learning, activation, applied linguistics, activation methods, teacher, student.

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy ta'lim nafaqat bilimlarni uzatish, balki talabalarda o'rganish uchun barqaror motivatsiya, tanqidiy fikrlash va tadqiqot tashabbusini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Talabalarning kognitiv faolligini faollashtirish amaliy tilshunoslikni o'qitish doirasida ayniqsa dolzarb bo'lib, bu talabalardan til jarayonlarini tahlil qilish va bilimlarni amaliy qo'llashda faol ishtirok etishni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kognitiv faoliyat, innovatsion ta'lim, faollashtirish, amaliy tilshunoslik, faollashtirish usullari, o'qituvchi, talaba.

Активизация познавательной деятельности – ключ к развитию самостоятельности мышления, повышению учебной мотивации и формированию профессиональных компетенций.

Как отмечает Н.Р. Мадаминава: «Применение различных технологий и методов для активизации познавательной деятельности студентов позволяет не только формировать познавательные, но и профессиональные мотивы и интересы, воспитывать системное мышление специалиста» [3, 213].

Познавательная активность – это внутренняя готовность и стремление учащегося к самостоятельному поиску, осмыслению и усвоению знаний. Она проявляется в умении задавать вопросы, анализировать, делать выводы и применять полученные знания на практике. В условиях высшего образования преподаватель должен создавать такие условия, при которых студент становится

не пассивным потребителем информации, а её активным создателем и интерпретатором.

Как мы отмечали в предыдущих статьях, педагог сегодня должен понять, что «инновационное образование – это способ воспитания гармоничной личности. Инновационные методики характеризуются новым стилем организации учебно-познавательной деятельности учеников» [1, 333-334].

Говоря об особенностях прикладной лингвистики, необходимо отметить, что она включает в себя изучение теоретических основ языка и их применение в различных сферах: переводе, лексикографии, компьютерной лингвистике, языкознании и обучении языку. Она ориентирована на решение практических задач, что делает дисциплину особенно подходящей для применения активных форм обучения. Студенты могут работать с реальными текстами, языковыми корпусами, цифровыми инструментами анализа, что стимулирует интерес и вовлекает в исследовательскую деятельность.

Ранее мы писали, что на занятиях в вузе можно применять такие современные модели обучения, как flipped classroom («перевернутый класс») и blended learning («смешанное обучение»)» [2, 499].

Для повышения познавательной активности на занятиях по прикладной лингвистике эффективно использовать следующие методы:

Проблемное обучение: формулировка исследовательских задач, требующих самостоятельного поиска решений (например, анализ языковых ошибок в машинном переводе). Оно способствует развитию критического мышления и исследовательских навыков.

Проектная работа: выполнение мини-исследований по актуальным темам (создание словаря терминов, разработка обучающего приложения). В результате развиваются самостоятельность, навыки анализа и представления результатов.

Кейс-метод: анализ и решение реальных ситуаций (например, выбор адекватной языковой модели для автоматической обработки текста).

Работа в малых группах: дискуссия, мозговые штурмы, ролевые игры. Это способствует развитию коммуникативных навыков.

Использование цифровых ресурсов: анализ текстов с помощью программ (AntConc, Sketch Engine), работа с корпусами и электронными словарями. В результате данной работы прослеживается связь между теорией и практикой, развивается интерес к анализу «живого» языка, а также вырабатываются навыки цифровой грамотности.

В частности, на занятиях по прикладной лингвистике можно предложить следующие типы заданий:

1) сравнить перевод текста (например, новостной статьи) с помощью Google Translate, DeepL и ChatGPT с целью выявить лексико-грамматические и стилистические ошибки, предложить улучшения. Данный вид работы развивает аналитическое мышление, навыки редактирования, практическое применение теории;

2) используя национальный корпус русского (или английского) языка, исследовать частотность и контексты употребления слова (например, «влияние») с целью выявить стилистическую окраску, жанровые особенности. Это развивает навыки анализа реальных языковых данных;

3) составить тематический глоссарий (например, терминов интернет-коммуникации) с определениями и примерами из практики с целью систематизации и интерпретации профессиональной лексики, что способствует развитию лексикографических навыков, а также улучшает работу с источниками;

4) обратный перевод (Back Translation), к примеру, выполнить перевод текста с русского на английский, затем перевести его обратно и сравнить с оригиналом с целью обнаружить и обсудить смысловые и стилистические потери. Данный вид работы развивает внимательность к нюансам языка, а также улучшает переводческие навыки.

Преподаватель в этом процессе выполняет функции организатора, консультанта и модератора. Он направляет учебный процесс, формулирует цели, задаёт проблемные вопросы и помогает студентам самостоятельно выстраивать траекторию обучения. Важно создавать атмосферу доверия, открытости и поощрять инициативу студентов.

Сегодня в связи с повсеместным использованием Интернета в процессе обучения широко применяются также электронные образовательные ресурсы: платформа LearningApps, Kahoot, Online Test Pad [2, 500], которые можно активно использовать для подготовки различных заданий по закреплению материала по направлениям прикладной лингвистики, тем самым активизируя познавательную деятельность студентов и их включение в процесс обучения.

Как отмечают авторы статьи, по итогам анализа многочисленных трудов по проблеме использования информационных технологий в учебном процессе, «можно утверждать, что для развития у студентов творческого мышления, памяти, активизации познавательной деятельности необходима модернизация процесса преподавания и использование мультимедийных средств обучения» [4, 2].

Из всего вышеуказанного можно сделать вывод о том, что активизация познавательной деятельности студентов в рамках прикладной лингвистики требует целенаправленного использования современных педагогических

технологий, цифровых ресурсов и интерактивных форм работы. Только при условии активного вовлечения студентов в учебный процесс можно сформировать устойчивые знания и профессиональные навыки, необходимые в будущей деятельности лингвиста.

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ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ МЕДИАДИСКУРСА В УСЛОВИЯХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНОГО МЕДИА

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Аннотация: В данной работе рассматривается влияние глобализации информационного пространства на распространение английского языка и трансформацию медийных дискурсов в англоязычных и русскоязычных медиа. Анализируется, как английский язык, ставший универсальной lingua franca, оказывает воздействие на формат, содержание и стилистику медиапродукции в медиаконтентах. Работа опирается на междисциплинарный подход, объединяющий методы лингвистического анализа, медиакритики и культурологических исследований, и направлена на выявление специфики межъязыкового и межкультурного взаимодействия в современной медиасреде.

Ключевые слова: медиадискурс, глобализация, медиапродукция, медиаконтент, современная медиасреда.

Abstract: This paper examines the impact of globalization of the information space on the spread of the English language and the transformation of media discourses in English-language and Russian-language media. It analyzes how the English language, which has become a universal lingua franca, influences the format, content and style of media products in media content. The work is based

on an interdisciplinary approach that combines the methods of linguistic analysis, media criticism and cultural studies, and is aimed at identifying the specifics of interlingual and intercultural interaction in the modern media environment.

Keywords: media discourse, globalization, media products, media content, modern media environment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada axborot makonining globallashuvining ingliz tilining tarqalishiga ta'siri va ingliz va rus tilidagi ommaviy axborot vositalarida media-diskurslarning o'zgarishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada universal tilga aylangan ingliz tilining media-kontentdagi media-mahsulotlar formati, mazmuni va uslubiga qanday ta'sir etishi tahlil qilinadi. Ish lingvistik tahlil, mediatanqid va madaniyatshunoslik usullarini o'zida mujassam etgan fanlararo yondashuvga asoslangan bo'lib, zamonaviy media muhitida tillararo va madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sirning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: media-diskurs, globallashuv, media-mahsulotlar, media-kontent, zamonaviy media muhiti.

Глобализация информационного пространства оказала существенное влияние на глобальное распространение английского языка, превратив его в универсальное средство межнационального общения, *lingua franca*¹¹¹. Сегодня английский язык занимает лидирующие позиции в международном бизнесе, торговле, политике, дипломатии, науке, информационных технологиях, СМИ, музыке, шоу-бизнесе, спорте и образовании, что делает его незаменимым инструментом в практически каждой сфере человеческой деятельности. Постоянное развитие и изменения, поддерживающие язык в динамическом состоянии, являются залогом его жизнеспособности. Как заметила Кэтрин Коннор Мартин, руководитель американского отдела словарей Oxford University Press, прекращение изменений в английском языке приведёт к его «смерти» и превращению в латынь. С появлением интернета скорость языковых трансформаций достигла небывалых высот: специализированная лексика, сленг и новые термины становятся доступными широкой аудитории, а сообщество пользователей активно формирует и распространяет их посредством таких ресурсов, как Google Ngram. Например, лингвист Дэвид Кристал отмечал, что число случаев написания слова «gubarb» выросло с нескольких сотен в 2006 году до почти 100 000 в 2010, а затем достигло примерно 750 000 случаев, что демонстрирует глубокое влияние цифровых технологий на орфографию и лексику¹¹². Эти процессы отражают, как объединение глобального информационного пространства с передовыми цифровыми технологиями способствует не только динамике языковых изменений, но и формированию

¹¹¹ Добросклонская Т.Г. Медиалингвистика: системный подход к изучению языка СМИ. М. 2008.

¹¹² Crystal D. Internet Linguistics: A Student Guide. — Routledge. New York. 2011.

единой системы массовых коммуникаций, которая активно влияет на культурное и лингвокультурное развитие современного общества¹¹³.

В условиях глобализации влияние англо-американских средств массовой информации на русские медиа становится особенно заметным как в форматах и содержании, так и в языковых практиках. Западные образцы телевизионной и радиопродукции, широко представленные в англоязычном медиaprостранстве, активно используются в русских медиа через лицензионное и пиратское копирование форматов, мощную волну заимствований и имитацию характерных коммуникативно-вещательных стилей. Это явление проявляется, например, в том, что многие популярные проекты российского телевидения являются адаптированными аналогами известных западных программ¹¹⁴. Так, «Маска» выступает как лицензированный вариант программы «The Masked Show», а «Слабое звено» – как российская интерпретация английского формата «The Weakest Link». Помимо этого, форматы, характерные для англоязычных масс медиа, такие как ток-шоу, викторины, телефонные программы, скрытые камеры, программы исповедей и реалити-шоу, успешно интегрируются в медиасферу и демонстрируют устойчивый рост использования в странах СНГ.

Не менее важным аспектом является не только заимствование форматов, но и адаптация содержания. Многие русскоязычные издания, освещающие мировые новости кино, популярной музыки и события в мире шоу-бизнеса, часто «перекачивают» материалы с англоязычных интернет-ресурсов, таких как сайты, аналогичные «Hello!», при этом практически исчезает практика указания на источники из зарубежной прессы. Эта тенденция отражает общий процесс унификации медийного дискурса, когда формирование и передача информации осуществляется с использованием общих международных стандартов. Более того, значительную роль в современном медиадискурсе играет активное использование так называемого информационно-вещательного стиля, который представляет собой особый тон общения с аудиторией, применяемый различными СМИ – от печатных изданий до телеканалов и радиопередач. Каждый медиасубъект «разговаривает» со своими читателями или зрителями посредством устойчивых стилистических и риторических механизмов, выбор которых варьируется в зависимости от политического, исторического, культурного, идеологического и социального контекста. Например, официальный тон телевизионных новостей RT отличается от объективного стиля

¹¹³ Favilla J. E. A World Without Whom. Bloomsbury, NY. 2017 —p. 16-17

¹¹⁴ Boyd-Barret O. Media Imperialism: towards an international framework for the analysis of media systems. Ch. 5 in Mass Communication and Society. London, 1977, p.251

вещания ВВС, а развлекательные программы зачастую характеризуются неформальностью¹¹⁵.

Изучая взаимовлияние англоязычного и русскоязычного медиадискурсов, нельзя не отметить и роль русского языка в формировании англоязычного медийного пространства, хотя его влияние бывает менее заметным, чем обратное явление. Одним из ярких примеров является пресса, предназначенная для экспатриантов, то есть медиа, ориентированные на русскоговорящих граждан, проживающих за рубежом, а также на иностранцев, интересующихся жизнью в странах СНГ. К таким изданиям можно отнести, например, газеты «The Moscow Times» и «The Russian Profile», которые выпускаются в Европе или Северной Америке, предоставляя материалы о русской реальности для аудитории, владеющей английским языком. Анализ таких источников показывает, что тексты мгновенно адаптируются к доминирующему лингвокультурному окружению, включают в себя наиболее распространённые и значимые лексические единицы, отражающие особенности национальной культуры¹¹⁶.

Работая в рамках русскоязычного культурного контекста, англоязычные медиа не только передают информацию о событиях мирового масштаба, но и тщательно освещают новости регионального характера, что побуждает корреспондентов использовать оригинальные русские слова для сохранения национального колорита в своих материалах¹¹⁷. Так, например, в англоязычных публикациях о российских культурных и социальных явлениях слово «babushka» используется без перевода, поскольку оно передаёт не только семейную принадлежность, как «grandmother» или «granny», но и содержит богатый спектр дополнительных коннотаций, характерных для русской культуры. Подобная языковая практика обусловлена намеренным выбором иностранных журналистов, которые при описании регионального опыта стремятся не только сохранить аутентичность передаваемой информации, но и подчеркнуть межкультурные различия. Использование русских терминов в англоязычных текстах имеет четкое мотивационное обоснование, поскольку позволяет читателям глубже понять специфику национального контекста. Это отражает тенденцию современной медиаиндустрии, где интеграция лингвокультурных элементов становится важным инструментом для создания уникальной стилистики и эмоциональной насыщенности материалов.

В итоге, явление заимствования и адаптации форматов, содержания и лингвистических элементов свидетельствует о глубокой интеграции глобальных

¹¹⁵ Добросклонская Т.Г. Медиалингвистика: системный подход к изучению языка СМИ. М. 2008. - стр.10-11

¹¹⁶ Добросклонская Т.Г. Медиалингвистика: системный подход к изучению языка СМИ. М. 2008. - стр. 13-15

¹¹⁷ Лаптева О.А. «Живая русская речь с телеэкрана», М., УРСС, 2000, стр.3

медиа-тенденций в медиасфере, где английский и русский языковые коды взаимодействуют в рамках единой информационной среды. Это взаимодействие играет ключевую роль в формировании современного общественного сознания, способствуя созданию уникальной смеси глобального и национального, когда медиа становятся не только каналом передачи информации, но и ареной для межкультурного диалога, отражающего сложные процессы глобализации и локальной идентичности.

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ МЕТАФОРИЧЕСКИХ ГЛАГОЛОВ ДВИЖЕНИЯ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются функционально-семантические особенности метафорических глаголов движения *идти бормок келмоқ* в русском и узбекском языках, частоупотребляемые при репрезентации континуума пространственно-временных феноменов. Раскрывается потенциал объективируемых глаголов движения при метафоризации концептуальной картины мира, исследуются динамика трансформации и механизм их перекодирования в новое содержание, при котором переносное значение играет ключевую роль.

Ключевые слова: агенс, пациенс, глаголы движения, каузация движения, метафорическая модель, семантическая роль, способ движения, эмоция.

Abstract. The article examines the functional and semantic features of metaphorical verbs of motion, *go bormok kelmok*, in Russian and Uzbek, often used to represent the continuum of spatio-temporal phenomena. The potential of objectified verbs of motion is revealed in the metaphorization of the conceptual picture of the world, the dynamics of transformation and the mechanism of their recoding into new content are studied, in which the figurative meaning plays a key role.

Key words: agent, patient, verbs of motion, causation of motion, metaphorical model, semantic role, mode of movement, emotion.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada rus va o'zbek tillarida ko'pincha fazo-vaqt hodisalarining uzluksizligini ifodalashda qo'llaniladigan harakat, go bormoq kelmoq metaforik fe'llarining funksional va semantik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Dunyoning kontseptual rasmini metaforizatsiya qilishda ob'ektivlashtirilgan harakat fe'llarining imkoniyatlari ochib beriladi, o'zgarish dinamikasi va ularni yangi mazmunga qayta kodlash mexanizmi o'rganiladi, bunda majoziy ma'no asosiy rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: agent, bemor, harakat fe'llari, harakat sababi, metaforik model, semantik rol, harakat usuli, his-tuyg'u.

В мировых языках метафора является одним из форм художественного отражения картины мира. При метафоризации упор делается на сходство между предметами или явлениями, что делает язык богатой и выразительной. Метафора пронизывает все сферы деятельности человека является наиболее эффективным средством общественной коммуникации.

Обзор литературы

Исследованиями метафоризации занимались множество ученых. Ю.Д. Апресян подчеркивает что теоретический интерес к метафоре « ... был стимулирован увеличением ее присутствия в различных видах текстов, начиная с поэтической речи и публицистики и кончая языками разных отраслей научного знания. Естественно, что экспансия метафоры в разные виды дискурса не прошла незамеченной. Искусствоведы, философы и психологи, науковеды и лингвисты обратились к проблеме метафоры с возросшим интересом»[1]

М. Блэк, касаясь условий появления метафоры, подчеркивает «В живой речи большую помощь нам могут оказать эмфаза и интонация. Но в письменном или печатном тексте нет даже этих минимальных показателей. А ведь эта ускользящая “сила” имеет огромное практическое значение в толковании метафоры» [2].

По мнению Г.А. Бучиной, «Экстралингвистические и собственно лингвистические факторы обуславливают степень продуктивности использования метафорического способа наименования в отдельных подсистемах исследуемых систем»[3].

Как подчеркивает Дж. Лакофф , М. Джонсон «Понятия, управляющие нашим мышлением, вовсе не замыкаются в сфере интеллекта. Они управляют также нашей повседневной деятельностью, включая самые обыденные, земные ее детали. Наши понятия упорядочивают воспринимаемую нами реальность, способы нашего поведения в мире и наши контакты с людьми. Наша понятийная система играет, таким образом, центральную роль в определении повседневной реальности. И если мы правы в своем предположении, что наша понятийная система носит преимущественно метафорический характер, тогда наше мышление, повседневный опыт и поведение в значительной степени обуславливаются метафорой» [5].

Методология исследования

Данное исследование, построенное на анализе материала метафорических глаголов двух языков раскрывает метафорический потенциал глаголов движения в двух языках, выявляет универсальные и дифференциальные их особенности, способствующие проследит процесс формирования необычной концептуально-знаковой системы.

В статье использованы основные методы исследования – описательный и сопоставительный, метод лингвистического моделирования.

Анализ и результаты

Метафорические глаголы *итди* в русском языке, *bormoq kelmoq* в узбекском имеют свои отличительные содержательные пометы, что объясняется культурно-ментальными особенностями носителей лингвистической знаковой системы. При метафоризации происходит перекодирование прямого значения в переносное, когда появляется новый мир слова со своими непростыми семантическими, стилистическими отношениями.

Новые производные метафорические глаголы перестраивают глагольную парадигму, строят новые семантическую структуру, Метафоризация является своеобразным каузатором развития всякого языка. Каузация один из основных атрибутов пульсирующего процесса метафоризации. Можно утверждать нет каузации нет метафоры. Поэтому каузирующий элемент метафоризации находит свое отражении в работах исследователей как обязательный ее атрибут.

В процессе исследования выявлено, что глаголы движения *идти бормоқ келмоқ* часто присутствуют в метафорических моделях, обозначающих пространственно-временные значения: *время идет, снег идет vaqt o'tyapni qor kelyapti*.

В контексте метафоры в русском языке глагол *идти* обозначает:

темпоральный отрезок *часыдут, время идет, жизнь идет;*

процессуальный признак *идет гроза, идет сон идет строительство, мясо идет в пищу, идет служба в армии, товар идет хорошо, идет фильм. лед идет, идет операция идет дискуссия,*

качественный признак *платье идет тебе*

пространственный признак *тропа идет через лес, самолет идет на посадку*

Как видим, элативный глагол движения представлен в нескольких метафорических моделях, репрезентирующих различную каузативную ситуации, сформировавшейся в условиях сложной дистрибуции концепта к своему конечному знаковому выражению.

Содержание глагола *идти* в узбекском языке имеет соответствующие формы *бормоқ келмоқ*, которые могут трансформироваться в приставочные глаголы *пойти прийти*, но при этом синтаксические структуры в которых они задействованы требуют обязательно предложно-падежных инструментариев, определяющих адекватность семантических показателей.

На концептуальном уровне при образовании метафоры акт каузации обязательна. На знаковом уровне складывается иная картина. В конструкциях непереходных элативных метафорических глаголов каузация отсутствует. В переходных метафорических глаголах движения каузация является консолидирующим атрибутом. Различая категории концептов и категорию лингвистической системы знаков, нужно отметить отсутствие каузации в метафорических вариантах элативного глагола *идти* в обоих языках.

Метафорические глаголы движения *идти* (*зайти прийти выйти уйти* и т.д.) и их аналоги в узбекском языке *келмоқ, бормоқ* (*кирмоқ, келмоқ, чиқмоқ кетмоқ* и др.) представлены в обоих языках несколькими метафорическими моделями, репрезентирующие пространственно-временную структуру. В формировании этой группы модели принимают участие ряд актантов. На знаковом уровне целостной структуры метафоризации глаголов данными основными элементами выступают агенс, пациенс и сам глагол. Другими словами в формировании глагольной метафоры участвуют метафоризированный агенс и его метафоризированное действие, неметафоризованный агенс с действием в прямом значении, а также основание метафоризации

Объективируемые метафорические глаголы используются при описании направления движения в обоих рассматриваемых языках. При этом семантический спектр метафорических глаголов разнообразен, который требует специального исследования. Этот факт является хорошим подтверждением того, что движение во времени и пространстве, является образцом для концептуализации характера движения. При этом, как показывает исследования материала, наиболее часто метафорические глаголы движения используются при описании времени, пространства, процесса и качества. Но при этом частотность образования метафоры различаются по своим направлениям движения. Например: сверху вниз; снизу вверх; снаружи внутрь, изнутри наружу, а также множества других направлений в пространстве.

Заклучение

В статье обобщаются наблюдений над метафорическими глаголами движения узбекского и русского языков. В частности, изучены универсальные свойства метафоризации глаголов *идти* в русском языке, *бормоқ, келмоқ* в узбекском.

Метафорические глаголы движения в обоих языках имеют свои семантические и функциональные особенности. Они принимают участие в концептуализации пространства, времени и других категорий, понятийных атрибутов и т.д. в данных языках, которые актуализируют универсальные стратегии в метафорическом использовании глаголов.

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ЗАИМСТВОВАННЫЕ СЛОВА В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ: ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ЭТАПЫ ЗАИМСТВОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются исторические этапы заимствования слов в русском языке, начиная с древних времен и заканчивая современным периодом. Анализируются причины заимствований, их влияние на развитие языка и особенности адаптации заимствованных слов. Исследование основывается на исторических данных, примерах заимствований из различных языков и анализе их употребления в русском языке.

Ключевые слова: заимствованные слова, русский язык, исторические этапы, лексика, иностранные влияния, языковые контакты.

Annotation. This article examines the historical stages of borrowing words in the Russian language, from ancient times to the modern period. The reasons for borrowings, their influence on language development, and the peculiarities of adaptation of borrowed words are analyzed. The study is based on historical data, examples of borrowings from various languages, and an analysis of their use in Russian.

Keywords: borrowed words, Russian language, historical stages, vocabulary, foreign influences, linguistic contacts.

Русский язык на протяжении всей своей истории активно взаимодействовал с другими языками, что привело к заимствованию значительного количества слов. Эти заимствования происходили на разных исторических этапах и были обусловлены культурными, экономическими, политическими и технологическими факторами¹¹⁸. В данной статье рассматриваются основные периоды заимствования, их особенности и влияние на русский язык.

1. *Древнейшие заимствования (до XIV века)*. На первых этапах формирования русского языка происходило заимствование слов из древнеславянских, финно-угорских, тюркских и греческих языков¹¹⁹. Эти слова связаны с торговлей, религией и бытом: *тюркские заимствования*: такие слова, как «арба» (телега), «караван», «базар», «сарай»¹²⁰; *греческие заимствования* (особенно через принятие христианства в X веке): «икона», «ангел», «крест», «патриарх»; *скандинавские заимствования* (через варягов): «кнут», «ярл».

2. *Заимствования эпохи Московского государства (XV–XVII века)*. В этот период усиливаются контакты с Западной Европой и Востоком. Русский язык пополняется словами из польского, немецкого, итальянского, французского и голландского языков: *польские заимствования* (через влияние Речи Посполитой): «пан», «шляхтич», «казна»; *немецкие и голландские заимствования* (в связи с развитием армии и флота): «шлюпка», «гаубица», «бутылка»; *итальянские заимствования* (архитектура, искусство): «палаццо», «балкон».

3. *Петровская эпоха и XVIII век*. При Петре I российское государство активно заимствовало западноевропейские слова, особенно из голландского, немецкого, английского и французского языков. Это связано с реформами в армии, флоте, науке и культуре: *голландские и немецкие заимствования*: «шлюп», «яхта», «верфь», «парад»; *французские заимствования* (влияние французской культуры и моды): «кавалер», «галантный», «маркиз»; *английские заимствования* (позднее, в конце XVIII века): «спорт», «комфорт»

4. *XIX век: влияние французского и немецкого языков*. XIX век характеризуется массовым проникновением французской лексики в русский язык, особенно в аристократических кругах¹²¹. Также продолжается влияние немецкого языка, особенно в технической и научной сферах: *французские*

¹¹⁸ Зализняк А. А. Очерки по истории русского языка. – М.: Русский язык, 2006.

¹¹⁹ Горбаневский М. В. Русский язык и языковые контакты. – СПб.: Филологический факультет СПбГУ, 2005.

¹²⁰ Фасмер М. Этимологический словарь русского языка. – М.: Прогресс, 1986.

¹²¹ Трубачев О. Н. Историческая морфология русского языка. – М.: Издательство АН СССР, 1959.

заимствования: «меню», «гарсон», «парфюм», «интрига»; немецкие заимствования: «штраф», «курс», «штаб».

5. XX век: англоязычные заимствования и советская эпоха. XX век стал периодом интенсивного заимствования слов из английского языка, особенно после Второй мировой войны и в эпоху научно-технического прогресса: английские заимствования: «футбол», «джинсы», «компьютер», «маркетинг»; заимствования советского периода: во время СССР происходило активное освоение интернациональных слов, например, «трактор», «пионер», «революция».

6. Современный период (XXI век). Сегодня русский язык продолжает заимствовать слова, главным образом из английского, в сферах информационных технологий, бизнеса, поп-культуры¹²²: «флешмоб», «стартап», «вебинар», «контент». Активно развиваются кальки и гибридные заимствования: «гуглить», «лайкать».

Заключение. Заимствованные слова играют важную роль в развитии русского языка, обогащая его лексику и способствуя адаптации к изменениям в обществе и науке. Исторические этапы заимствования отражают динамику культурных и политических связей России с другими странами¹²³. Несмотря на опасения о чрезмерном влиянии иностранных слов, русский язык сохраняет свою уникальность, усваивая и адаптируя заимствования в соответствии со своими законами.

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¹²² Крысин Л. П. Иноязычные слова в современном русском языке. – М.: Наука, 1996.

¹²³ Виноградов В. В. История русского языка. – М.: Наука, 1978.

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